

Unified Study of Narcissistic Numbers without and with Division¹

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Abstract

This paper brings unified study of narcissistic numbers without and with division. This work is in done in two parts. One for without division and second for with division. It is combination of author's previous two works [17, 19]. The previous are seperated in different situations, while this one com together.

Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Fixed and Flexible Power Narcissistic Numbers	4
2.1	Single Digit Numbers	4
2.2	Two Digits Numbers	4
2.3	Three Digits Numbers	4
2.4	Four Digits Numbers	5
2.5	Four Digits Numbers	17
3	Fixed and Flexible Power Narcissistic Numbers with Division	150
3.1	Single Digit Numbers	150
3.2	Two Digits Numbers	150
3.3	Three Digits Numbers	150
3.4	Four Digits Numbers	163
3.5	Five Digits Numbers	320
3.6	Six Digits and More	345

¹This work is combined and unified version of author's previous two works
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1 Introduction

An n -digit number that is the sum of the n^{th} powers of its digits is called an n -narcissistic number. It is also sometimes known as an Armstrong number, perfect digital invariant (Madachy 1966 [6]), or plus perfect number. Hardy in 1940 [2] (pg. 25) wrote, there are just four numbers of three digits, which are the sums of the cubes of their digits:

$$\begin{aligned}153 &= 1^3 + 5^3 + 3^3 \\370 &= 3^3 + 7^3 + 0^3 \\371 &= 3^3 + 7^3 + 1^3 \\407 &= 4^3 + 0^3 + 7^3\end{aligned}$$

The above four numbers have the same digits on both sides except the power 3 and are with 3 digits. There are four more numbers with 4 digits:

$$\begin{aligned}1634 &:= 1^4 + 6^4 + 3^4 + 4^4 \\4151 &:= 4^5 + 1^5 + 5^5 + 1^5 \\8208 &:= 8^4 + 2^4 + 0^4 + 8^4 \\9472 &:= 9^4 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 2^4\end{aligned}$$

Above numbers are with fixed power. Relaxing this condition, we many have much numbers with flexible power, for example,

$$\begin{aligned}132 &:= 1^1 + 3^1 + 2^7 \\2353 &:= 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 3^7\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

Moreover, instead of having positive coefficients, we can have positive-negative coefficients, for example,

$$\begin{aligned}128 &:= -1^1 + 2^7 + 8^0 \\9942 &:= -9^1 - 9^4 + 4^7 + 2^7\end{aligned}\tag{2}$$

The following four numbers are known in the literature [3, 4, 5]:

$$\begin{aligned}3435 &:= 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5 \\438579088 &:= 4^4 + 3^3 + 8^8 + 5^5 + 7^7 + 9^9 + 0^0 + 8^8 + 8^8 \\48625 &:= 4^5 + 8^2 + 6^6 + 2^8 + 5^4 \\397612 &:= 3^2 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 6^7 + 1^9 + 2^3\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

The first two are having the same power as of bases. The last two numbers are such that the power is in reverse order of digits numbers. Our aim here is little different. We want to bring numbers similar to one given in (1) and (2), where only the bases follows the digit's order, and the powers are flexible both for positive, and positive-negative coefficients. The work is limited up to 5 digits. The numbers 3435 and 48625 appearing in (3) are also appears in our study. The number 397612 appears in author's another work [17]. The only number left 438579088 is for further study.

Let's consider the following expression:

$$abc\dots = a^{m_1} \pm b^{m_2} \pm c^{m_3} \pm \dots, a, b, c, \dots \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}, a \neq 0. \quad (4)$$

For simplicity, let us write the (4) as

$$abc\dots = (a, b, d, \dots)^{(m_1, m_2, m_3, \dots)} \quad (5)$$

Detailed study of numbers arising due to equation (4) or (5) are given in [16, 17]. If the powers and bases are of same digits with different permutations, then the equation (5) can be re-written as

$$abc\dots = (a, b, d, \dots)^{(a, b, c, \dots)} \quad (6)$$

Numbers arising due to (6) are defined as **permutable powers selfie numbers**, and studied by author [17]. See below some examples,

$$\begin{aligned} 23 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 \\ 1364 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3 \\ 3435 &:= 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5 \\ 3045 &:= -3^4 + 0^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 \\ 78205 &:= 7^2 - 8^0 + 2^5 + 0^8 + 5^7 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

From (7), we observe that the powers and bases are of same digits with different permutations. For detailed study of this work refer author's work [17]. Study on numbers in different situations see summary of author's work [14, 15]. The **flexible power narcissistic numbers** can be seen in author's recent work [12].

Let's extend the expression (4) with division:

$$abc\dots = \frac{a^{m_1} \pm b^{m_2} \pm c^{m_3} \pm \dots}{a^{n_1} \pm b^{n_2} \pm c^{n_3} \pm \dots}, a, b, c, \dots \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}, a \neq 0. \quad (8)$$

The above construction (7), we call **flexible power narcissistic numbers with division**. The powers are always natural numbers, and it may be flexible. Also, instead having positive coefficients, we may have positive and negative coefficients. In some situations, this general way include the previous known results. Relaxing some conditions, the above **narcissistic numbers** can also be re-written in terms of division. See below:

$$\begin{aligned} 153 &:= \frac{1^3 + 5^3 + 3^3}{1^0 + 5^0 - 3^0} & 1634 &:= \frac{1^4 + 6^4 + 3^4 + 4^4}{-1^0 - 6^0 - 3^0 + 4^1} \\ 370 &:= \frac{3^3 + 7^3 + 0^3}{3^0 + 7^0 - 0^0} & 4151 &:= \frac{4^5 + 1^5 + 5^5 + 1^5}{-4^1 + 1^1 + 5^1 - 1^1} \\ 371 &:= \frac{3^3 + 7^3 + 1^3}{3^0 + 7^0 - 1^0} & 8208 &:= \frac{8^4 + 2^4 + 0^4 + 8^4}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 8^0} \\ 407 &:= \frac{4^3 + 0^3 + 7^3}{4^0 + 0^0 - 7^0} & 9472 &:= \frac{9^4 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 2^4}{9^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 2^2} \end{aligned}$$

In this work, aim is to write **narcissistic without and with division**. This is done extending the work given above. It is combined study of author's previous works [17, 18, 19].

2 Fixed and Flexible Power Narcissistic Numbers

2.1 Single Digit Numbers

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 1 := 1^1 & 3 := 3^1 & 5 := 5^1 & 7 := 7^1 & 9 := 9^1 \\
 2 := 2^1 & 4 := 4^1 & 6 := 6^1 & 8 := 8^1 &
 \end{array}$$

2.2 Two Digits Numbers

$$\begin{array}{ccc}
 23 := -2^2 + 3^3 & 43 := 4^2 + 3^3 & 63 := 6^2 + 3^3 \\
 24 := 2^3 + 4^2 & 48 := -4^2 + 8^2 & 89 := 8^1 + 9^2
 \end{array}$$

2.3 Three Digits Numbers

$$\begin{array}{cccc}
 125 := -1^1 + 2^0 + 5^3 & 238 := -2^2 + 3^5 - 8^0 & 264 := 2^1 + 6^1 + 4^4 & 370 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 0^1 \\
 126 := -1^1 + 2^7 - 6^0 & 240 := -2^4 + 4^4 + 0^1 & 264 := -2^3 + 6^4 - 4^5 & 371 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 1^0 \\
 128 := -1^1 + 2^7 + 8^0 & 241 := -2^4 + 4^4 + 1^0 & 267 := 2^1 + 6^3 + 7^2 & 372 := -3^1 + 7^3 + 2^5 \\
 132 := 1^1 + 3^1 + 2^7 & 242 := -2^4 + 4^4 + 2^1 & 278 := -2^6 + 7^3 - 8^0 & 372 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 2^1 \\
 135 := 1^1 + 3^2 + 5^3 & 243 := -2^2 + 4^1 + 3^5 & 283 := 2^5 + 8^1 + 3^5 & 373 := 3^1 + 7^3 + 3^3 \\
 152 := -1^1 + 5^2 + 2^7 & 244 := -2^3 - 4^1 + 4^4 & 283 := -2^8 + 8^3 + 3^3 & 374 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 4^1 \\
 153 := 1^1 + 5^3 + 3^3 & 245 := -2^4 + 4^4 + 5^1 & 287 := -2^6 + 8^1 + 7^3 & 375 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 5^1 \\
 175 := 1^1 + 7^2 + 5^3 & 246 := -2^2 + 4^4 - 6^1 & 308 := 3^5 + 0^0 + 8^2 & 375 := -3^5 - 7^1 + 5^4 \\
 209 := 2^7 + 0^1 + 9^2 & 247 := -2^1 + 4^4 - 7^1 & 317 := -3^3 + 1^0 + 7^3 & 376 := -3^1 + 7^3 + 6^2 \\
 222 := -2^1 - 2^5 + 2^8 & 248 := -2^3 - 4^4 + 8^3 & 332 := 3^4 + 3^5 + 2^3 & 376 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 6^1 \\
 223 := -2^2 - 2^4 + 3^5 & 249 := -2^3 + 4^4 + 9^0 & 333 := 3^2 + 3^4 + 3^5 & 377 := 3^3 + 7^1 + 7^3 \\
 224 := -2^4 - 2^4 + 4^4 & 254 := 2^7 + 5^3 + 4^0 & 334 := -3^1 + 3^4 + 4^4 & 378 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 8^1 \\
 224 := 2^5 + 2^7 + 4^3 & 258 := 2^8 + 5^0 + 8^0 & 334 := 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^3 & 379 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 9^1 \\
 225 := -2^5 + 2^8 + 5^0 & 262 := 2^7 + 6^1 + 2^7 & 337 := -3^1 - 3^1 + 7^3 & 392 := -3^4 + 9^3 - 2^8 \\
 226 := 2^1 + 2^3 + 6^3 & 262 := -2^8 + 6^1 + 2^9 & 347 := 3^1 + 4^0 + 7^3 & 397 := -3^3 + 9^2 + 7^3 \\
 234 := -2^3 + 3^5 - 4^0 & 263 := -2^4 + 6^2 + 3^5 & 354 := -3^3 + 5^3 + 4^4 & 407 := 4^3 + 0^1 + 7^3 \\
 236 := -2^3 + 3^5 + 6^0 & 263 := 2^8 + 6^1 + 3^0 & 357 := 3^2 + 5^1 + 7^3 & 427 := -4^7 + 2^2 + 7^5
 \end{array}$$

$445 := 4^3 + 4^4 + 5^3$	$557 := -5^4 - 5^6 + 7^5$	$694 := -6^2 + 9^3 + 4^0$	$934 := -9^1 - 3^4 + 4^5$
$448 := -4^3 + 4^5 - 8^3$	$574 := -5^2 + 7^3 + 4^4$	$723 := -7^1 + 2^0 + 3^6$	$935 := 9^2 + 3^6 + 5^3$
$463 := 4^1 + 6^3 + 3^5$	$597 := -5^3 + 9^3 - 7^1$	$725 := -7^4 + 2^0 + 5^5$	$936 := -9^1 + 3^6 + 6^3$
$487 := -4^7 + 8^2 + 7^5$	$598 := 5^1 + 9^2 + 8^3$	$737 := 7^1 + 3^6 + 7^0$	$942 := -9^2 + 4^5 - 2^0$
$488 := -4^2 - 8^1 + 8^3$	$629 := 6^2 + 2^9 + 9^2$	$739 := 7^1 + 3^1 + 9^3$	$944 := -9^2 + 4^0 + 4^5$
$508 := -5^1 + 0^0 + 8^3$	$629 := -6^2 - 2^6 + 9^3$	$779 := 7^2 + 7^0 + 9^3$	$946 := 9^3 + 4^0 + 6^3$
$518 := 5^1 + 1^0 + 8^3$	$665 := -6^1 + 6^4 - 5^4$	$794 := 7^2 + 9^3 + 4^2$	$973 := 9^3 + 7^0 + 3^5$
$538 := 5^2 + 3^0 + 8^3$	$692 := -6^2 + 9^3 - 2^0$	$849 := 8^3 + 4^4 + 9^2$	$994 := 9^1 + 9^3 + 4^4$

2.4 Four Digits Numbers

$1022 := -1^1 - 0^0 + 2^9 + 2^9$	$1296 := -1^1 + 2^1 - 9^0 + 6^4$	$1542 := 1^1 + 5^1 + 4^5 + 2^9$
$1024 := -1^1 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 4^5$	$1306 := 1^1 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 6^4$	$1546 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 4^4 + 6^4$
$1034 := 1^1 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 4^5$	$1323 := 1^1 + 3^4 + 2^9 + 3^6$	$1563 := -1^1 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 3^5$
$1042 := 1^1 + 0^0 + 4^5 + 2^4$	$1326 := 1^1 + 3^3 + 2^1 + 6^4$	$1569 := -1^1 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 9^3$
$1073 := 1^1 + 0^1 + 7^3 + 3^6$	$1326 := -1^1 - 3^0 + 2^5 + 6^4$	$1584 := -1^1 + 5^4 - 8^2 + 4^5$
$1074 := 1^1 + 0^1 + 7^2 + 4^5$	$1327 := -1^1 + 3^6 + 2^8 + 7^3$	$1632 := -1^1 + 6^4 + 3^4 + 2^8$
$1232 := -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 2^9$	$1329 := -1^1 + 3^6 - 2^7 + 9^3$	$1634 := 1^1 + 6^4 + 3^4 + 4^4$
$1234 := 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^5$	$1349 := 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^5 + 9^2$	$1637 := -1^1 + 6^4 - 3^0 + 7^3$
$1234 := -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^5 + 4^5$	$1354 := -1^1 + 3^6 + 5^4 + 4^0$	$1638 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 3^7 - 8^3$
$1236 := -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 6^4$	$1356 := 1^1 + 3^6 + 5^4 + 6^0$	$1654 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 4^5$
$1238 := -1^1 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 8^3$	$1362 := 1^1 + 3^0 + 6^4 + 2^6$	$1672 := 1^1 + 6^4 + 7^3 + 2^5$
$1239 := -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^0 + 9^3$	$1362 := -1^1 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 2^6$	$1672 := -1^1 - 6^3 + 7^4 - 2^9$
$1243 := 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^0 + 3^6$	$1364 := 1^1 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3$	$1676 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 7^3 + 6^4$
$1254 := -1^1 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 4^5$	$1368 := -1^1 + 3^2 + 6^4 + 8^2$	$1723 := -1^1 + 7^2 - 2^9 + 3^7$
$1255 := 1^1 + 2^2 + 5^4 + 5^4$	$1386 := -1^1 + 3^3 + 8^2 + 6^4$	$1765 := 1^1 + 7^3 + 6^4 + 5^3$
$1256 := -1^1 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^4$	$1386 := 1^1 + 3^4 + 8^1 + 6^4$	$1806 := -1^1 + 8^3 - 0^0 + 6^4$
$1262 := -1^1 - 2^0 + 6^4 - 2^5$	$1426 := 1^1 + 4^0 + 2^7 + 6^4$	$1836 := 1^1 + 8^3 + 3^3 + 6^4$
$1264 := -1^1 - 2^5 + 6^4 + 4^0$	$1498 := 1^1 + 4^4 + 9^3 + 8^3$	$1856 := -1^1 - 8^2 + 5^4 + 6^4$
$1286 := -1^1 - 2^0 - 8^1 + 6^4$	$1526 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 2^8 + 6^4$	$1872 := -1^1 - 8^3 + 7^4 - 2^4$
		$1879 := -1^1 - 8^3 + 7^4 - 9^1$
		$1887 := -1^1 - 8^0 - 8^3 + 7^4$

$$\begin{aligned} 1897 &:= -1^1 - 8^3 + 9^1 + 7^4 \\ 1927 &:= -1^1 - 9^3 + 2^8 + 7^4 \\ 2033 &:= -2^7 + 0^0 - 3^3 + 3^7 \\ 2043 &:= -2^7 + 0^1 - 4^2 + 3^7 \\ 2044 &:= -2^2 + 0^1 + 4^5 + 4^5 \\ 2048 &:= 2^9 + 0^1 + 4^5 + 8^3 \\ 2053 &:= -2^3 - 0^0 - 5^3 + 3^7 \\ 2064 &:= -2^8 + 0^1 + 6^4 + 4^5 \\ 2064 &:= 2^9 + 0^1 + 6^4 + 4^4 \\ 2073 &:= -2^6 - 0^0 - 7^2 + 3^7 \\ 2123 &:= -2^6 + 1^0 - 2^0 + 3^7 \\ 2132 &:= -2^6 + 1^0 + 3^7 + 2^3 \\ 2133 &:= -2^6 + 1^0 + 3^2 + 3^7 \\ 2137 &:= -2^8 + 1^0 - 3^2 + 7^4 \\ 2139 &:= -2^7 - 1^0 + 3^7 + 9^2 \\ 2147 &:= -2^8 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 7^4 \\ 2153 &:= -2^3 - 1^0 - 5^2 + 3^7 \\ 2173 &:= -2^3 + 1^0 - 7^1 + 3^7 \\ 2176 &:= -2^3 - 1^0 + 7^4 - 6^3 \\ 2183 &:= -2^1 - 1^0 - 8^0 + 3^7 \\ 2193 &:= -2^1 - 1^0 + 9^1 + 3^7 \\ 2193 &:= 2^2 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 3^7 \\ 2203 &:= 2^3 + 2^3 + 0^1 + 3^7 \\ 2203 &:= -2^4 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 3^7 \\ 2223 &:= 2^1 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 3^7 \\ 2223 &:= -2^2 + 2^3 + 2^5 + 3^7 \\ 2234 &:= -2^4 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^3 \\ 2236 &:= 2^4 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 6^0 \\ 2236 &:= -2^4 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2243 &:= -2^2 - 2^2 + 4^3 + 3^7 \\ 2243 &:= 2^3 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 3^7 \\ 2249 &:= -2^4 + 2^9 + 4^5 + 9^3 \\ 2253 &:= 2^6 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 3^7 \\ 2263 &:= 2^3 + 2^5 + 6^2 + 3^7 \\ 2263 &:= -2^4 + 2^7 - 6^2 + 3^7 \\ 2264 &:= -2^6 + 2^3 + 6^4 + 4^5 \\ 2264 &:= 2^9 + 2^9 + 6^3 + 4^5 \\ 2267 &:= -2^6 - 2^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\ 2270 &:= -2^1 - 2^7 + 7^4 - 0^0 \\ 2271 &:= -2^7 - 2^0 + 7^4 - 1^0 \\ 2272 &:= -2^1 - 2^7 + 7^4 + 2^0 \\ 2273 &:= -2^7 - 2^0 + 7^4 + 3^0 \\ 2274 &:= -2^6 - 2^6 + 7^4 + 4^0 \\ 2275 &:= -2^7 + 2^0 + 7^4 + 5^0 \\ 2276 &:= -2^7 + 2^1 + 7^4 + 6^0 \\ 2278 &:= -2^7 + 2^2 + 7^4 + 8^0 \\ 2283 &:= 2^4 + 2^4 + 8^2 + 3^7 \\ 2283 &:= -2^5 + 2^6 + 8^2 + 3^7 \\ 2286 &:= -2^1 - 2^9 + 8^4 - 6^4 \\ 2303 &:= -2^7 + 3^5 + 0^0 + 3^7 \\ 2305 &:= -2^3 + 3^7 + 0^0 + 5^3 \\ 2312 &:= -2^1 + 3^7 - 1^0 + 2^7 \\ 2314 &:= -2^7 + 3^7 - 1^0 + 4^4 \\ 2315 &:= 2^1 + 3^7 + 1^0 + 5^3 \\ 2317 &:= -2^1 - 3^4 - 1^0 + 7^4 \\ 2317 &:= 2^7 + 3^7 + 1^0 + 7^0 \\ 2320 &:= 2^2 + 3^7 + 2^7 + 0^0 \\ 2324 &:= 2^3 + 3^7 + 2^7 + 4^0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2327 &:= -2^6 - 3^2 - 2^0 + 7^4 \\ 2332 &:= 2^3 + 3^2 + 3^7 + 2^7 \\ 2332 &:= -2^6 + 3^4 + 3^7 + 2^7 \\ 2333 &:= -2^4 + 3^4 + 3^4 + 3^7 \\ 2333 &:= 2^6 + 3^0 + 3^4 + 3^7 \\ 2334 &:= 2^1 + 3^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 \\ 2334 &:= -2^7 - 3^1 + 3^8 - 4^6 \\ 2335 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 + 3^7 + 5^3 \\ 2336 &:= 2^5 + 3^4 + 3^7 + 6^2 \\ 2336 &:= -2^6 - 3^1 + 3^7 + 6^3 \\ 2337 &:= -2^6 + 3^0 - 3^0 + 7^4 \\ 2337 &:= -2^6 - 3^0 + 3^0 + 7^4 \\ 2343 &:= 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 3^7 \\ 2345 &:= 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 5^3 \\ 2347 &:= -2^6 + 3^2 + 4^0 + 7^4 \\ 2352 &:= 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 2^5 \\ 2353 &:= -2^4 - 3^3 + 5^5 - 3^6 \\ 2353 &:= 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 3^7 \\ 2354 &:= -2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 4^4 \\ 2355 &:= -2^4 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 5^5 \\ 2356 &:= -2^2 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\ 2356 &:= 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^2 \\ 2357 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^2 \\ 2365 &:= -2^5 - 3^6 + 6^0 + 5^5 \\ 2367 &:= -2^3 - 3^3 + 6^0 + 7^4 \\ 2370 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 + 7^4 + 0^1 \\ 2371 &:= -2^1 - 3^3 + 7^4 - 1^0 \\ 2372 &:= -2^2 - 3^2 + 7^4 - 2^4 \\ 2372 &:= 2^3 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 2^7 \\ 2373 &:= -2^1 - 3^3 + 7^4 + 3^0 \\ 2373 &:= 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^2 + 3^7 \\ 2374 &:= -2^1 - 3^2 + 7^4 - 4^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2375 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 + 7^4 + 5^1 \\ 2376 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 + 7^4 + 6^1 \\ 2376 &:= 2^3 + 3^6 + 7^3 + 6^4 \\ 2377 &:= -2^1 + 3^3 - 7^2 + 7^4 \\ 2378 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\ 2379 &:= -2^2 - 3^2 + 7^4 - 9^1 \\ 2380 &:= 2^7 + 3^7 + 8^2 + 0^0 \\ 2386 &:= -2^4 + 3^7 - 8^0 + 6^3 \\ 2387 &:= -2^2 - 3^2 - 8^0 + 7^4 \\ 2392 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 + 9^2 + 2^7 \\ 2395 &:= -2^1 + 3^0 - 9^3 + 5^5 \\ 2395 &:= 2^1 + 3^7 + 9^2 + 5^3 \\ 2396 &:= -2^3 + 3^7 + 9^0 + 6^3 \\ 2396 &:= 2^7 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^4 \\ 2397 &:= -2^1 - 3^0 - 9^0 + 7^4 \\ 2397 &:= 2^7 + 3^7 + 9^2 + 7^0 \\ 2398 &:= -2^6 - 3^1 + 9^4 - 8^4 \\ 2407 &:= 2^1 + 4^1 + 0^1 + 7^4 \\ 2423 &:= -2^2 - 4^2 + 2^8 + 3^7 \\ 2427 &:= 2^1 + 4^2 + 2^3 + 7^4 \\ 2427 &:= -2^1 - 4^1 + 2^5 + 7^4 \\ 2429 &:= -2^2 - 4^6 - 2^5 + 9^4 \\ 2432 &:= -2^5 - 4^6 + 3^8 - 2^0 \\ 2433 &:= 2^1 + 4^0 + 3^5 + 3^7 \\ 2434 &:= -2^3 - 4^0 + 3^7 + 4^4 \\ 2436 &:= -2^3 + 4^4 + 3^7 + 6^0 \\ 2436 &:= 2^5 + 4^0 + 3^7 + 6^3 \\ 2437 &:= 2^3 + 4^0 + 3^3 + 7^4 \\ 2443 &:= -2^2 + 4^1 + 4^4 + 3^7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2443 &:= 2^7 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 3^7 \\ 2445 &:= -2^1 - 4^5 + 4^6 - 5^4 \\ 2447 &:= -2^1 - 4^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 \\ 2449 &:= -2^5 + 4^2 - 4^6 + 9^4 \\ 2463 &:= -2^2 + 4^3 + 6^3 + 3^7 \\ 2464 &:= -2^5 - 4^7 - 6^6 + 4^8 \\ 2464 &:= 2^7 + 4^2 + 6^4 + 4^5 \\ 2467 &:= -2^2 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\ 2467 &:= 2^6 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 7^4 \\ 2469 &:= -2^1 - 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\ 2470 &:= 2^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 0^0 \\ 2473 &:= -2^3 - 4^0 + 7^4 + 3^4 \\ 2474 &:= 2^3 + 4^0 + 7^4 + 4^3 \\ 2479 &:= -2^1 - 4^0 + 7^4 + 9^2 \\ 2483 &:= 2^5 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 3^7 \\ 2485 &:= -2^6 - 4^3 - 8^3 + 5^5 \\ 2517 &:= -2^3 + 5^3 - 1^0 + 7^4 \\ 2532 &:= 2^6 + 5^2 + 3^7 + 2^8 \\ 2533 &:= -2^9 + 5^5 - 3^4 + 3^0 \\ 2536 &:= 2^3 + 5^3 + 3^7 + 6^3 \\ 2537 &:= 2^1 + 5^1 + 3^7 + 7^3 \\ 2537 &:= -2^4 + 5^3 + 3^3 + 7^4 \\ 2552 &:= -2^9 - 5^3 + 5^5 + 2^6 \\ 2572 &:= -2^9 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 2^3 \\ 2573 &:= -2^9 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 3^2 \\ 2574 &:= -2^4 + 5^3 + 7^4 + 4^3 \\ 2574 &:= 2^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 + 4^2 \\ 2576 &:= -2^4 - 5^2 + 7^4 + 6^3 \\ 2577 &:= 2^1 + 5^3 + 7^2 + 7^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2578 &:= -2^9 + 5^4 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\ 2582 &:= -2^5 + 5^5 - 8^3 + 2^0 \\ 2596 &:= -2^4 + 5^5 - 9^3 + 6^3 \\ 2615 &:= -2^9 + 6^0 + 1^0 + 5^5 \\ 2626 &:= 2^1 + 6^4 + 2^5 + 6^4 \\ 2627 &:= 2^1 + 6^3 + 2^3 + 7^4 \\ 2637 &:= -2^3 + 6^0 + 3^5 + 7^4 \\ 2643 &:= -2^4 + 6^3 + 4^4 + 3^7 \\ 2645 &:= -2^3 - 6^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\ 2647 &:= -2^2 - 6^1 + 4^4 + 7^4 \\ 2649 &:= -2^5 + 6^3 - 4^6 + 9^4 \\ 2650 &:= -2^9 + 6^2 + 5^5 + 0^0 \\ 2652 &:= -2^8 - 6^3 + 5^5 - 2^0 \\ 2654 &:= -2^8 - 6^3 + 5^5 + 4^0 \\ 2664 &:= 2^3 + 6^4 + 6^4 + 4^3 \\ 2669 &:= -2^2 + 6^4 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\ 2674 &:= 2^4 + 6^0 + 7^4 + 4^4 \\ 2687 &:= -2^6 - 6^4 + 8^4 - 7^2 \\ 2695 &:= -2^9 + 6^0 + 9^2 + 5^5 \\ 2707 &:= 2^8 + 7^2 + 0^0 + 7^4 \\ 2722 &:= 2^6 + 7^4 + 2^0 + 2^8 \\ 2727 &:= -2^4 + 7^3 - 2^0 + 7^4 \\ 2732 &:= -2^4 + 7^2 + 3^7 + 2^9 \\ 2732 &:= 2^5 + 7^0 + 3^7 + 2^9 \\ 2733 &:= 2^3 + 7^4 + 3^4 + 3^5 \\ 2734 &:= -2^2 + 7^4 + 3^4 + 4^4 \\ 2735 &:= -2^2 + 7^3 - 3^6 + 5^5 \\ 2735 &:= 2^7 + 7^4 + 3^4 + 5^3 \\ 2736 &:= -2^7 - 7^4 + 3^8 - 6^4 \\ 2736 &:= 2^9 + 7^0 + 3^7 + 6^2 \\ 2737 &:= -2^2 + 7^3 - 3^1 + 7^4 \\ 2738 &:= 2^5 + 7^1 + 3^7 + 8^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2738 &:= -2^8 + 7^4 + 3^4 + 8^3 \\ 2739 &:= 2^7 + 7^3 + 3^7 + 9^2 \\ 2739 &:= -2^7 - 7^2 + 3^7 + 9^3 \\ 2746 &:= 2^7 + 7^4 + 4^0 + 6^3 \\ 2747 &:= 2^1 + 7^3 + 4^0 + 7^4 \\ 2750 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 0^1 \\ 2751 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 1^0 \\ 2752 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 2^1 \\ 2753 &:= -2^1 - 7^3 + 5^5 - 3^3 \\ 2753 &:= 2^9 + 7^2 + 5^1 + 3^7 \\ 2754 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 4^1 \\ 2755 &:= -2^1 - 7^3 - 5^2 + 5^5 \\ 2756 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\ 2757 &:= 2^3 + 7^3 + 5^1 + 7^4 \\ 2757 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\ 2758 &:= -2^4 - 7^3 + 5^5 - 8^1 \\ 2759 &:= -2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 2765 &:= -2^4 - 7^3 - 6^0 + 5^5 \\ 2772 &:= -2^2 + 7^3 + 7^4 + 2^5 \\ 2773 &:= 2^1 + 7^3 + 7^4 + 3^3 \\ 2775 &:= -2^3 + 7^0 - 7^3 + 5^5 \\ 2776 &:= -2^2 + 7^3 + 7^4 + 6^2 \\ 2777 &:= -2^4 + 7^2 + 7^3 + 7^4 \\ 2777 &:= 2^5 + 7^0 + 7^3 + 7^4 \\ 2778 &:= -2^7 - 7^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\ 2779 &:= -2^3 - 7^3 + 7^4 + 9^3 \\ 2786 &:= -2^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 6^0 \\ 2793 &:= -2^1 - 7^5 - 9^2 + 3^9 \\ 2794 &:= 2^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2795 &:= -2^8 + 7^1 - 9^2 + 5^5 \\ 2805 &:= -2^8 - 8^2 + 0^1 + 5^5 \\ 2823 &:= -2^2 + 8^3 + 2^7 + 3^7 \\ 2843 &:= 2^7 + 8^3 + 4^2 + 3^7 \\ 2843 &:= -2^8 + 8^4 - 4^5 + 3^3 \\ 2845 &:= -2^4 - 8^1 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\ 2847 &:= -2^1 + 8^3 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\ 2849 &:= -2^7 + 8^3 - 4^6 + 9^4 \\ 2852 &:= -2^4 - 8^0 + 5^5 - 2^8 \\ 2859 &:= -2^8 - 8^0 + 5^5 - 9^1 \\ 2862 &:= -2^1 + 8^4 - 6^4 + 2^6 \\ 2863 &:= 2^7 + 8^3 + 6^2 + 3^7 \\ 2864 &:= 2^5 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^5 \\ 2873 &:= -2^1 - 8^0 - 7^5 + 3^9 \\ 2875 &:= -2^8 - 8^0 + 7^1 + 5^5 \\ 2885 &:= -2^8 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 5^5 \\ 2913 &:= -2^1 + 9^3 - 1^0 + 3^7 \\ 2915 &:= -2^7 - 9^2 - 1^0 + 5^5 \\ 2932 &:= 2^3 + 9^3 + 3^7 + 2^3 \\ 2932 &:= -2^4 + 9^3 + 3^7 + 2^5 \\ 2933 &:= 2^3 + 9^1 + 3^6 + 3^7 \\ 2933 &:= -2^6 + 9^2 + 3^6 + 3^7 \\ 2934 &:= 2^1 + 9^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 \\ 2936 &:= -2^4 + 9^3 + 3^7 + 6^2 \\ 2950 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 0^1 \\ 2951 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 1^0 \\ 2952 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 2^1 \\ 2953 &:= 2^5 + 9^3 + 5^1 + 3^7 \\ 2953 &:= -2^6 - 9^2 + 5^5 - 3^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2954 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 4^1 \\ 2955 &:= -2^6 - 9^2 - 5^2 + 5^5 \\ 2956 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\ 2957 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\ 2958 &:= -2^8 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\ 2959 &:= -2^2 - 9^2 + 5^5 - 9^2 \\ 2973 &:= 2^3 + 9^3 + 7^2 + 3^7 \\ 2978 &:= -2^4 + 9^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\ 2978 &:= 2^6 + 9^0 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\ 2993 &:= -2^2 + 9^2 + 9^3 + 3^7 \\ 2994 &:= 2^9 + 9^3 + 9^3 + 4^5 \\ 2995 &:= -2^7 - 9^0 - 9^0 + 5^5 \\ 3035 &:= -3^2 + 0^1 - 3^4 + 5^5 \\ 3044 &:= -3^3 - 0^0 - 4^5 + 4^6 \\ 3045 &:= -3^4 + 0^1 + 4^0 + 5^5 \\ 3052 &:= -3^2 + 0^1 + 5^5 - 2^6 \\ 3053 &:= -3^4 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 3^2 \\ 3058 &:= -3^1 + 0^1 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\ 3125 &:= -3^1 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 5^5 \\ 3145 &:= 3^1 + 1^0 + 4^2 + 5^5 \\ 3147 &:= 3^6 + 1^0 + 4^2 + 7^4 \\ 3154 &:= 3^3 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 4^0 \\ 3165 &:= 3^1 + 1^0 + 6^2 + 5^5 \\ 3167 &:= 3^6 + 1^0 + 6^2 + 7^4 \\ 3185 &:= -3^1 - 1^0 + 8^2 + 5^5 \\ 3212 &:= 3^7 + 2^9 + 1^0 + 2^9 \\ 3214 &:= 3^7 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 4^5 \\ 3215 &:= 3^4 + 2^3 + 1^0 + 5^5 \\ 3225 &:= -3^3 - 2^0 + 2^7 + 5^5 \\ 3234 &:= -3^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^5 \\ 3235 &:= -3^1 + 2^5 + 3^4 + 5^5 \\ 3235 &:= 3^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 5^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3236 &:= -3^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 6^4 \\ 3237 &:= 3^4 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 7^4 \\ 3238 &:= 3^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 8^3 \\ 3238 &:= -3^6 - 2^7 - 3^0 + 8^4 \\ 3240 &:= -3^6 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 0^0 \\ 3244 &:= 3^7 + 2^5 + 4^0 + 4^5 \\ 3245 &:= -3^2 + 2^7 + 4^0 + 5^5 \\ 3250 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 0^1 \\ 3251 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 1^0 \\ 3252 &:= -3^1 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 2^7 \\ 3253 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 3^1 \\ 3254 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 4^1 \\ 3254 &:= 3^4 + 2^5 + 5^5 + 4^2 \\ 3255 &:= 3^1 + 2^1 + 5^3 + 5^5 \\ 3255 &:= -3^1 + 2^3 + 5^3 + 5^5 \\ 3256 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\ 3257 &:= 3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 \\ 3257 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\ 3258 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\ 3259 &:= -3^1 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 3274 &:= 3^6 + 2^7 + 7^4 + 4^2 \\ 3275 &:= -3^3 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 5^5 \\ 3292 &:= 3^7 + 2^9 + 9^2 + 2^9 \\ 3294 &:= -3^2 - 2^6 - 9^3 + 4^6 \\ 3294 &:= 3^7 + 2^1 + 9^2 + 4^5 \\ 3295 &:= 3^4 + 2^3 + 9^2 + 5^5 \\ 3324 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 - 2^4 + 4^6 \\ 3324 &:= 3^4 + 3^7 + 2^5 + 4^5 \\ 3325 &:= -3^2 + 3^4 + 2^7 + 5^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3325 &:= 3^7 + 3^0 + 2^9 + 5^4 \\ 3340 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 0^1 \\ 3341 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 1^0 \\ 3342 &:= 3^1 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 2^7 \\ 3342 &:= -3^2 - 3^6 + 4^6 - 2^4 \\ 3343 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 3^1 \\ 3344 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 4^6 \\ 3345 &:= 3^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 \\ 3345 &:= -3^2 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^5 \\ 3346 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\ 3347 &:= -3^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 7^1 \\ 3348 &:= -3^1 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 8^4 \\ 3349 &:= -3^2 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 9^3 \\ 3356 &:= -3^4 + 3^8 - 5^5 + 6^0 \\ 3364 &:= -3^2 - 3^6 + 6^1 + 4^6 \\ 3365 &:= -3^1 + 3^3 + 6^3 + 5^5 \\ 3366 &:= -3^4 + 3^7 - 6^2 + 6^4 \\ 3374 &:= 3^5 + 3^6 + 7^4 + 4^0 \\ 3382 &:= -3^6 - 3^0 + 8^4 + 2^4 \\ 3384 &:= -3^6 + 3^0 + 8^4 + 4^2 \\ 3385 &:= 3^2 + 3^5 + 8^1 + 5^5 \\ 3385 &:= -3^2 - 3^5 + 8^3 + 5^5 \\ 3417 &:= -3^2 + 4^5 + 1^0 + 7^4 \\ 3429 &:= 3^7 + 4^0 + 2^9 + 9^3 \\ 3432 &:= 3^6 + 4^1 + 3^7 + 2^9 \\ 3432 &:= -3^6 + 4^6 + 3^0 + 2^6 \\ 3434 &:= -3^6 + 4^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 \\ 3435 &:= 3^1 + 4^3 + 3^5 + 5^5 \\ 3435 &:= -3^3 + 4^4 + 3^4 + 5^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3436 &:= 3^2 + 4^5 + 3^7 + 6^3 \\ 3436 &:= -3^5 - 4^6 - 3^0 + 6^5 \\ 3437 &:= 3^1 + 4^5 + 3^2 + 7^4 \\ 3439 &:= -3^2 + 4^6 - 3^6 + 9^2 \\ 3449 &:= -3^6 + 4^0 + 4^6 + 9^2 \\ 3452 &:= -3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 2^3 \\ 3453 &:= -3^2 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 3^4 \\ 3453 &:= 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 3^5 \\ 3454 &:= 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 4^4 \\ 3454 &:= -3^4 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 4^6 \\ 3456 &:= -3^6 + 4^5 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\ 3457 &:= -3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\ 3457 &:= 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\ 3458 &:= -3^2 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 8^4 \\ 3459 &:= -3^1 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 9^2 \\ 3472 &:= -3^4 + 4^5 + 7^4 + 2^7 \\ 3473 &:= -3^4 + 4^5 + 7^3 + 3^7 \\ 3474 &:= 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^1 + 4^5 \\ 3475 &:= 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 5^5 \\ 3475 &:= -3^2 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 5^5 \\ 3476 &:= 3^7 + 4^5 + 7^2 + 6^3 \\ 3477 &:= 3^1 + 4^5 + 7^2 + 7^4 \\ 3479 &:= -3^3 + 4^5 + 7^4 + 9^2 \\ 3492 &:= -3^1 + 4^6 - 9^3 + 2^7 \\ 3492 &:= 3^7 + 4^3 + 9^3 + 2^9 \\ 3496 &:= 3^7 + 4^1 + 9^1 + 6^4 \\ 3497 &:= -3^2 + 4^5 + 9^2 + 7^4 \\ 3522 &:= -3^5 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 2^9 \\ 3523 &:= 3^3 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 3^5 \\ 3524 &:= -3^6 + 5^3 + 2^5 + 4^6 \\ 3525 &:= 3^5 + 5^3 + 2^5 + 5^5 \\ 3527 &:= 3^3 + 5^5 + 2^5 + 7^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3528 &:= -3^4 + 5^2 - 2^9 + 8^4 \\ 3543 &:= -3^2 - 5^4 + 4^6 + 3^4 \\ 3543 &:= 3^4 + 5^5 + 4^4 + 3^4 \\ 3545 &:= -3^6 + 5^3 + 4^5 + 5^5 \\ 3546 &:= -3^2 - 5^3 - 4^6 + 6^5 \\ 3547 &:= -3^1 + 5^3 + 4^5 + 7^4 \\ 3549 &:= -3^1 - 5^4 + 4^6 + 9^2 \\ 3562 &:= -3^4 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 2^9 \\ 3566 &:= 3^2 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 6^3 \\ 3569 &:= 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\ 3583 &:= -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 + 3^3 \\ 3585 &:= -3^3 - 5^2 + 8^3 + 5^5 \\ 3612 &:= 3^7 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 2^7 \\ 3617 &:= -3^4 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 7^4 \\ 3624 &:= -3^6 + 6^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 \\ 3625 &:= 3^5 + 6^0 + 2^8 + 5^5 \\ 3634 &:= -3^1 - 6^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 \\ 3635 &:= -3^1 - 6^3 + 3^6 + 5^5 \\ 3635 &:= 3^3 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 5^3 \\ 3638 &:= -3^5 - 6^3 + 3^0 + 8^4 \\ 3639 &:= -3^6 - 6^1 - 3^7 + 9^4 \\ 3652 &:= 3^2 + 6^1 + 5^5 + 2^9 \\ 3656 &:= -3^6 - 6^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\ 3657 &:= -3^3 + 6^3 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\ 3657 &:= 3^7 + 6^4 + 5^3 + 7^2 \\ 3670 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 0^1 \\ 3671 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 1^0 \\ 3672 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 2^1 \\ 3673 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 3^1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3674 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 4^1 \\ 3674 &:= 3^5 + 6^1 + 7^4 + 4^5 \\ 3675 &:= -3^2 + 6^3 + 7^3 + 5^5 \\ 3676 &:= -3^3 + 6^1 + 7^4 + 6^4 \\ 3677 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 7^4 \\ 3678 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\ 3678 &:= 3^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\ 3679 &:= -3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 9^1 \\ 3687 &:= -3^2 + 6^4 - 8^0 + 7^4 \\ 3692 &:= 3^7 + 6^4 + 9^2 + 2^7 \\ 3697 &:= -3^2 + 6^4 + 9^1 + 7^4 \\ 3706 &:= 3^2 + 7^4 + 0^1 + 6^4 \\ 3723 &:= 3^4 + 7^4 + 2^9 + 3^6 \\ 3724 &:= -3^3 - 7^3 - 2^1 + 4^6 \\ 3724 &:= 3^7 + 7^0 + 2^9 + 4^5 \\ 3725 &:= 3^4 + 7^1 + 2^9 + 5^5 \\ 3726 &:= -3^1 + 7^4 + 2^5 + 6^4 \\ 3726 &:= 3^3 + 7^4 + 2^1 + 6^4 \\ 3728 &:= -3^2 - 7^3 - 2^4 + 8^4 \\ 3742 &:= -3^1 - 7^3 + 4^6 - 2^3 \\ 3743 &:= -3^2 - 7^3 + 4^6 - 3^0 \\ 3745 &:= -3^1 - 7^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 \\ 3746 &:= -3^6 + 7^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 \\ 3746 &:= 3^7 + 7^1 + 4^4 + 6^4 \\ 3748 &:= -3^2 - 7^3 + 4^1 + 8^4 \\ 3749 &:= -3^1 - 7^3 + 4^6 - 9^0 \\ 3749 &:= 3^5 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 9^2 \\ 3756 &:= 3^6 + 7^4 + 5^4 + 6^0 \\ 3764 &:= 3^1 + 7^4 + 6^4 + 4^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3765 &:= 3^4 + 7^3 + 6^3 + 5^5 \\ 3766 &:= -3^8 + 7^5 - 6^5 + 6^4 \\ 3768 &:= -3^5 - 7^2 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\ 3769 &:= -3^2 + 7^4 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\ 3782 &:= -3^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 + 2^5 \\ 3786 &:= -3^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 + 6^2 \\ 3786 &:= 3^4 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 6^4 \\ 3788 &:= -3^5 - 7^0 - 8^2 + 8^4 \\ 3822 &:= -3^5 + 8^4 - 2^5 + 2^0 \\ 3834 &:= -3^3 + 8^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 \\ 3835 &:= -3^3 + 8^1 + 3^6 + 5^5 \\ 3843 &:= -3^2 - 8^0 + 4^6 - 3^5 \\ 3844 &:= -3^5 - 8^1 - 4^0 + 4^6 \\ 3846 &:= -3^5 - 8^0 + 4^6 - 6^1 \\ 3848 &:= -3^5 - 8^0 - 4^1 + 8^4 \\ 3852 &:= -3^5 + 8^4 - 5^1 + 2^2 \\ 3853 &:= -3^2 + 8^1 + 5^5 + 3^6 \\ 3854 &:= -3^6 + 8^3 - 5^2 + 4^6 \\ 3855 &:= -3^5 + 8^4 + 5^0 + 5^0 \\ 3856 &:= 3^1 + 8^3 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\ 3859 &:= -3^1 + 8^1 + 5^5 + 9^3 \\ 3860 &:= -3^5 + 8^4 + 6^1 + 0^0 \\ 3862 &:= -3^5 + 8^4 + 6^0 + 2^3 \\ 3863 &:= -3^5 + 8^4 + 6^0 + 3^2 \\ 3872 &:= -3^2 + 8^4 - 7^3 + 2^7 \\ 3873 &:= -3^2 + 8^4 - 7^4 + 3^7 \\ 3875 &:= -3^1 + 8^4 - 7^3 + 5^3 \\ 3878 &:= -3^6 + 8^3 - 7^0 + 8^4 \\ 3880 &:= -3^6 + 8^3 + 8^4 + 0^0 \\ 3924 &:= -3^3 - 9^2 - 2^6 + 4^6 \\ 3940 &:= 3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 0^1 \\ 3941 &:= 3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 1^0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3942 &:= -3^2 - 9^2 + 4^6 - 2^6 \\ 3942 &:= 3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 2^1 \\ 3943 &:= 3^1 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 3^7 \\ 3943 &:= -3^4 - 9^2 + 4^6 + 3^2 \\ 3944 &:= 3^7 + 9^3 + 4^1 + 4^5 \\ 3945 &:= 3^3 + 9^3 + 4^3 + 5^5 \\ 3946 &:= 3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 6^1 \\ 3947 &:= 3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 7^1 \\ 3948 &:= -3^1 - 9^2 - 4^3 + 8^4 \\ 3948 &:= 3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 8^1 \\ 3949 &:= 3^7 + 9^1 + 4^5 + 9^3 \\ 3964 &:= -3^3 - 9^5 + 6^6 + 4^7 \\ 3982 &:= -3^4 - 9^0 + 8^4 - 2^5 \\ 3984 &:= -3^3 - 9^2 + 8^4 - 4^1 \\ 3987 &:= -3^3 - 9^2 + 8^4 - 7^0 \\ 3989 &:= -3^3 - 9^2 + 8^4 + 9^0 \\ 4024 &:= -4^3 + 0^1 - 2^3 + 4^6 \\ 4028 &:= -4^1 + 0^1 - 2^6 + 8^4 \\ 4034 &:= -4^3 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 4^6 \\ 4048 &:= -4^3 + 0^1 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\ 4053 &:= -4^1 - 0^0 - 5^6 + 3^9 \\ 4054 &:= -4^2 - 0^0 - 5^2 + 4^6 \\ 4058 &:= -4^3 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\ 4068 &:= -4^3 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\ 4074 &:= -4^2 + 0^0 - 7^1 + 4^6 \\ 4078 &:= -4^2 - 0^0 - 7^0 + 8^4 \\ 4080 &:= -4^2 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 0^0 \\ 4081 &:= -4^2 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 1^0 \\ 4082 &:= -4^2 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 2^0 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4083 &:= -4^1 + 0^1 + 8^4 - 3^2 \\ 4084 &:= -4^1 + 0^1 - 8^1 + 4^6 \\ 4085 &:= -4^2 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 5^1 \\ 4086 &:= -4^1 + 0^1 + 8^4 - 6^1 \\ 4087 &:= -4^2 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 7^1 \\ 4088 &:= -4^2 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 8^4 \\ 4089 &:= -4^2 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 9^1 \\ 4094 &:= -4^1 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 4^6 \\ 4098 &:= 4^6 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 8^0 \\ 4099 &:= 4^6 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 9^0 \\ 4102 &:= 4^6 + 1^0 + 0^0 + 2^2 \\ 4114 &:= 4^2 + 1^0 + 1^0 + 4^6 \\ 4132 &:= 4^6 + 1^0 + 3^1 + 2^5 \\ 4133 &:= 4^6 + 1^0 + 3^2 + 3^3 \\ 4136 &:= 4^6 + 1^0 + 3^1 + 6^2 \\ 4147 &:= 4^6 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 7^2 \\ 4150 &:= 4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 0^1 \\ 4151 &:= 4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 1^0 \\ 4152 &:= 4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 2^1 \\ 4153 &:= 4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 3^1 \\ 4154 &:= 4^1 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 4^5 \\ 4155 &:= 4^5 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 5^5 \\ 4156 &:= 4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\ 4157 &:= 4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\ 4158 &:= -4^3 + 1^0 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\ 4158 &:= 4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\ 4159 &:= 4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 4162 &:= 4^6 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 2^6 \\ 4173 &:= 4^6 + 1^0 + 7^2 + 3^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4179 &:= 4^6 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 9^2 \\ 4194 &:= 4^2 + 1^0 + 9^2 + 4^6 \\ 4208 &:= -4^2 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 8^4 \\ 4209 &:= 4^6 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 9^2 \\ 4224 &:= -4^1 + 2^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 \\ 4224 &:= 4^3 + 2^5 + 2^5 + 4^6 \\ 4225 &:= 4^6 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 5^3 \\ 4226 &:= 4^6 + 2^0 + 2^7 + 6^0 \\ 4227 &:= 4^6 + 2^1 + 2^7 + 7^0 \\ 4228 &:= -4^1 + 2^3 + 2^7 + 8^4 \\ 4228 &:= 4^1 + 2^6 + 2^6 + 8^4 \\ 4229 &:= 4^6 + 2^2 + 2^7 + 9^0 \\ 4234 &:= 4^6 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^0 \\ 4240 &:= 4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 0^1 \\ 4241 &:= 4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 1^0 \\ 4242 &:= 4^2 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 2^7 \\ 4243 &:= 4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 3^1 \\ 4243 &:= -4^3 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 3^5 \\ 4244 &:= 4^1 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 4^6 \\ 4245 &:= -4^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^2 \\ 4245 &:= 4^2 + 2^3 + 4^6 + 5^3 \\ 4246 &:= 4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\ 4246 &:= -4^3 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 \\ 4247 &:= 4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 7^1 \\ 4247 &:= -4^3 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 7^3 \\ 4248 &:= 4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 8^1 \\ 4249 &:= 4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 9^1 \\ 4249 &:= -4^3 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 9^3 \\ 4250 &:= 4^6 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 0^0 \\ 4254 &:= 4^6 + 2^5 + 5^3 + 4^0 \\ 4260 &:= 4^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 0^1 \\ 4261 &:= 4^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 1^0 \end{aligned}$$

$4262 := 4^6 + 2^1 + 6^2 + 2^7$	$4342 := 4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 2^1$	$4397 := 4^5 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 7^4$
$4263 := 4^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 3^1$	$4343 := 4^6 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 3^5$	$4403 := 4^3 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 3^5$
$4264 := 4^1 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 4^6$	$4344 := 4^1 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 4^6$	$4405 := 4^4 + 4^5 + 0^1 + 5^5$
$4264 := -4^2 - 2^5 + 6^3 + 4^6$	$4345 := 4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^1$	$4424 := 4^3 + 4^4 + 2^3 + 4^6$
$4265 := 4^6 + 2^3 + 6^2 + 5^3$	$4346 := 4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 6^1$	$4427 := -4^1 + 4^6 - 2^3 + 7^3$
$4265 := -4^6 + 2^9 - 6^5 + 5^6$	$4347 := 4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 7^1$	$4429 := -4^1 + 4^6 + 2^8 + 9^2$
$4266 := 4^6 + 2^7 + 6^1 + 6^2$	$4348 := 4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 8^1$	$4434 := 4^4 + 4^0 + 3^4 + 4^6$
$4267 := 4^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 7^1$	$4349 := 4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 9^1$	$4443 := 4^3 + 4^4 + 4^6 + 3^3$
$4268 := 4^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 8^1$	$4352 := -4^5 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 2^6$	$4447 := 4^1 + 4^1 + 4^6 + 7^3$
$4269 := 4^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$4352 := 4^6 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 2^7$	$4449 := 4^2 + 4^4 + 4^6 + 9^2$
$4274 := 4^6 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 4^0$	$4353 := -4^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 3^7$	$4449 := -4^3 - 4^5 - 4^5 + 9^4$
$4283 := -4^3 + 2^3 + 8^4 + 3^5$	$4353 := 4^4 + 3^5 + 5^5 + 3^6$	$4469 := 4^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^2$
$4284 := -4^1 - 2^6 + 8^4 + 4^4$	$4354 := 4^4 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 4^6$	$4472 := 4^6 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 2^5$
$4285 := -4^3 + 2^7 + 8^4 + 5^3$	$4355 := 4^5 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 5^5$	$4476 := 4^6 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 6^2$
$4285 := 4^5 + 2^7 + 8^1 + 5^5$	$4356 := -4^3 - 3^0 + 5^5 + 6^4$	$4485 := 4^4 + 4^6 + 8^1 + 5^3$
$4288 := 4^3 + 2^6 + 8^2 + 8^4$	$4357 := -4^4 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^4$	$4487 := -4^2 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 7^3$
$4288 := -4^3 - 2^8 + 8^3 + 8^4$	$4358 := 4^4 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 8^4$	$4553 := -4^7 + 5^5 + 5^6 + 3^7$
$4289 := -4^2 + 2^7 + 8^4 + 9^2$	$4359 := -4^2 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 9^4$	$4572 := 4^6 + 5^1 + 7^3 + 2^7$
$4289 := 4^3 + 2^7 + 8^4 + 9^0$	$4362 := 4^6 + 3^2 + 6^0 + 2^8$	$4573 := -4^2 + 5^0 + 7^4 + 3^7$
$4309 := -4^3 - 3^7 - 0^0 + 9^4$	$4365 := 4^6 + 3^5 + 6^0 + 5^2$	$4573 := 4^5 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 3^4$
$4316 := 4^6 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 6^3$	$4369 := -4^1 - 3^7 - 6^0 + 9^4$	$4574 := 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 + 4^5$
$4324 := -4^2 + 3^5 + 2^0 + 4^6$	$4372 := 4^6 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 2^5$	$4586 := -4^3 - 5^5 - 8^0 + 6^5$
$4332 := 4^6 + 3^3 + 3^4 + 2^7$	$4373 := 4^6 + 3^3 + 7^1 + 3^5$	$4594 := -4^4 + 5^2 + 9^3 + 4^6$
$4334 := -4^1 - 3^0 + 3^5 + 4^6$	$4374 := -4^3 - 3^0 + 7^3 + 4^6$	$4596 := -4^3 - 5^5 + 9^1 + 6^5$
$4335 := -4^3 + 3^7 + 3^7 + 5^2$	$4376 := 4^6 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 6^2$	$4599 := 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^3 + 9^3$
$4338 := -4^1 + 3^1 + 3^5 + 8^4$	$4378 := -4^3 + 3^1 + 7^3 + 8^4$	$4622 := 4^6 + 6^1 + 2^3 + 2^9$
$4339 := 4^6 + 3^4 + 3^4 + 9^2$	$4380 := 4^4 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 0^0$	$4623 := 4^6 + 6^1 + 2^9 + 3^2$
$4340 := 4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 0^1$	$4395 := -4^1 - 3^7 + 9^4 + 5^2$	$4624 := -4^4 + 6^4 - 2^9 + 4^6$
$4341 := 4^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 1^0$	$4396 := 4^6 + 3^1 + 9^2 + 6^3$	$4628 := -4^2 + 6^2 + 2^9 + 8^4$
		$4644 := 4^4 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 4^6$
		$4648 := 4^1 + 6^2 + 4^6 + 8^3$
		$4648 := -4^4 - 6^3 + 4^5 + 8^4$

$4649 := 4^4 + 6^3 + 4^6 + 9^2$	$4935 := -4^3 + 9^4 - 3^7 + 5^4$	$5325 := 5^1 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 5^5$
$4658 := -4^3 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 8^4$	$4950 := 4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 0^1$	$5326 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 6^1$
$4685 := 4^4 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 5^5$	$4951 := 4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 1^0$	$5327 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 7^1$
$4689 := -4^3 - 6^4 - 8^3 + 9^4$	$4952 := 4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 2^1$	$5328 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 8^1$
$4732 := 4^2 + 7^4 + 3^7 + 2^7$	$4952 := -4^6 - 9^4 + 5^6 - 2^4$	$5329 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 9^1$
$4733 := 4^2 + 7^3 + 3^7 + 3^7$	$4953 := 4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 3^1$	$5342 := 5^1 + 3^6 + 4^6 + 2^9$
$4735 := 4^5 + 7^3 + 3^5 + 5^5$	$4954 := 4^1 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 4^6$	$5343 := 5^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 3^7$
$4736 := 4^6 + 7^3 + 3^4 + 6^3$	$4955 := 4^6 + 9^3 + 5^1 + 5^3$	$5344 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 4^2$
$4737 := -4^3 + 7^4 - 3^0 + 7^4$	$4956 := 4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 6^1$	$5347 := -5^6 + 3^7 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$4738 := 4^6 + 7^2 + 3^4 + 8^3$	$4957 := 4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 7^1$	$5362 := -5^6 + 3^9 + 6^4 + 2^3$
$4754 := -4^2 + 7^2 + 5^4 + 4^6$	$4958 := 4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 8^1$	$5363 := -5^6 + 3^2 + 6^4 + 3^9$
$4776 := -4^4 - 7^3 - 7^4 + 6^5$	$4959 := 4^5 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 9^3$	$5364 := -5^2 - 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^6$
$4778 := -4^1 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 8^4$	$4959 := -4^6 - 9^1 + 5^6 - 9^4$	$5364 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 4^2$
$4787 := -4^2 + 7^4 + 8^0 + 7^4$	$4975 := -4^6 - 9^4 + 7^1 + 5^6$	$5365 := -5^2 + 3^8 - 6^4 + 5^3$
$4797 := -4^1 + 7^4 - 9^0 + 7^4$	$5162 := -5^5 - 1^0 + 6^5 + 2^9$	$5366 := 5^5 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 6^4$
$4809 := -4^2 + 8^4 + 0^1 + 9^3$	$5234 := 5^4 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 4^6$	$5367 := -5^1 - 3^1 + 6^5 - 7^4$
$4823 := -4^1 + 8^4 + 2^1 + 3^6$	$5236 := -5^2 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 6^4$	$5367 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 6^1 + 7^2$
$4826 := 4^6 + 8^3 + 2^1 + 6^3$	$5239 := -5^4 + 2^5 - 3^6 + 9^4$	$5368 := -5^2 + 3^0 + 6^4 + 8^4$
$4829 := -4^1 + 8^4 + 2^3 + 9^3$	$5258 := 5^2 + 2^9 + 5^4 + 8^4$	$5369 := -5^4 + 3^6 - 6^4 + 9^4$
$4830 := 4^1 + 8^4 + 3^6 + 0^0$	$5268 := -5^3 + 2^0 + 6^4 + 8^4$	$5384 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 8^1 + 4^3$
$4834 := 4^6 + 8^1 + 3^6 + 4^0$	$5274 := -5^6 - 2^2 + 7^5 + 4^6$	$5386 := -5^1 - 3^0 + 8^4 + 6^4$
$4848 := -4^2 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 8^4$	$5276 := 5^5 + 2^9 + 7^3 + 6^4$	$5394 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 9^2 + 4^0$
$4849 := 4^2 + 8^1 + 4^6 + 9^3$	$5295 := -5^4 - 2^4 + 9^4 - 5^4$	$5413 := -5^3 - 4^5 + 1^0 + 3^8$
$4864 := -4^2 - 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^6$	$5314 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 1^0 + 4^0$	$5423 := -5^4 - 4^0 - 2^9 + 3^8$
$4869 := 4^6 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 9^3$	$5320 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 0^1$	$5439 := -5^3 - 4^5 + 3^3 + 9^4$
$4887 := -4^3 + 8^3 + 8^4 + 7^3$	$5321 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 1^0$	$5446 := 5^5 + 4^0 + 4^5 + 6^4$
$4890 := 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^3 + 0^0$	$5322 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 2^1 + 2^3$	$5453 := 5^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 3^7$
$4932 := 4^6 + 9^2 + 3^5 + 2^9$	$5323 := 5^5 + 3^1 + 2^3 + 3^7$	$5457 := -5^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4$
$4933 := 4^6 + 9^2 + 3^3 + 3^6$	$5324 := 5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 4^1$	$5463 := -5^3 - 4^0 + 6^5 - 3^7$
		$5493 := -5^3 - 4^5 + 9^2 + 3^8$
		$5496 := -5^1 - 4^5 + 9^4 - 6^2$
		$5543 := -5^2 + 5^5 + 4^4 + 3^7$

$5547 := 5^1 + 5^5 + 4^2 + 7^4$	$5926 := -5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 6^1$	$6263 := -6^1 - 2^8 - 6^2 + 3^8$
$5563 := -5^2 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 3^7$	$5927 := -5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 7^1$	$6266 := -6^3 + 2^1 - 6^4 + 6^5$
$5567 := 5^1 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$5928 := -5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 8^1$	$6283 := -6^3 + 2^1 - 8^2 + 3^8$
$5639 := -5^4 - 6^3 - 3^4 + 9^4$	$5929 := -5^4 + 9^0 - 2^3 + 9^4$	$6289 := -6^3 + 2^3 - 8^2 + 9^4$
$5653 := 5^3 + 6^3 + 5^5 + 3^7$	$5934 := -5^4 - 9^0 + 3^8 - 4^0$	$6298 := -6^1 - 2^8 + 9^4 - 8^0$
$5657 := 5^3 + 6^1 + 5^5 + 7^4$	$5936 := -5^4 - 9^0 + 3^8 + 6^0$	$6313 := -6^1 - 3^5 + 1^0 + 3^8$
$5674 := -5^5 + 6^5 - 7^0 + 4^5$	$5938 := -5^4 + 9^0 + 3^8 + 8^0$	$6319 := -6^3 - 3^3 + 1^0 + 9^4$
$5693 := -5^4 - 6^3 + 9^4 - 3^3$	$5940 := -5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 0^1$	$6332 := -6^3 - 3^2 + 3^8 - 2^2$
$5695 := -5^2 - 6^3 + 9^4 - 5^4$	$5941 := -5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 1^0$	$6333 := -6^3 - 3^1 - 3^2 + 3^8$
$5729 := -5^4 + 7^2 - 2^8 + 9^4$	$5942 := -5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 2^1$	$6334 := -6^3 - 3^3 + 3^8 + 4^2$
$5746 := 5^5 + 7^4 + 4^1 + 6^3$	$5943 := -5^4 - 9^1 + 4^2 + 3^8$	$6335 := -6^3 - 3^2 + 3^8 - 5^0$
$5762 := -5^3 - 7^4 + 6^5 + 2^9$	$5944 := -5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 4^1$	$6336 := -6^1 - 3^1 + 3^8 - 6^3$
$5766 := 5^5 + 7^2 + 6^4 + 6^4$	$5945 := -5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 5^1$	$6337 := -6^3 - 3^0 + 3^8 - 7^1$
$5769 := -5^4 + 7^2 - 6^3 + 9^4$	$5946 := -5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 6^1$	$6338 := -6^1 - 3^6 + 3^8 + 8^3$
$5832 := 5^5 + 8^1 + 3^7 + 2^9$	$5947 := -5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 7^1$	$6339 := -6^1 + 3^3 - 3^5 + 9^4$
$5833 := 5^5 + 8^3 + 3^2 + 3^7$	$5948 := -5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 8^1$	$6342 := -6^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 2^0$
$5836 := -5^4 - 8^2 + 3^8 - 6^2$	$5949 := -5^4 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$6343 := -6^3 - 3^0 - 4^0 + 3^8$
$5858 := 5^4 + 8^3 + 5^4 + 8^4$	$5962 := -5^4 + 9^4 - 6^1 + 2^5$	$6345 := -6^3 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 5^0$
$5873 := -5^4 - 8^2 + 7^0 + 3^8$	$5963 := -5^4 - 9^1 + 6^2 + 3^8$	$6347 := -6^3 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^0$
$5873 := 5^5 + 8^3 + 7^2 + 3^7$	$5964 := -5^4 + 9^4 - 6^2 + 4^3$	$6349 := -6^3 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 9^4$
$5877 := 5^5 + 8^1 + 7^3 + 7^4$	$5966 := -5^4 + 9^4 - 6^1 + 6^2$	$6350 := -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 0^1$
$5879 := -5^4 - 8^1 - 7^2 + 9^4$	$5969 := -5^2 + 9^3 - 6^4 + 9^4$	$6351 := -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 1^0$
$5892 := -5^3 - 8^3 + 9^4 - 2^5$	$5988 := -5^3 + 9^4 - 8^3 + 8^2$	$6352 := -6^3 + 3^8 - 5^0 + 2^3$
$5920 := -5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 0^1$	$6226 := -6^4 + 2^1 - 2^8 + 6^5$	$6353 := -6^3 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 3^8$
$5921 := -5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 1^0$	$6236 := -6^4 - 2^0 - 3^5 + 6^5$	$6354 := -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 4^1$
$5922 := -5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 2^1$	$6243 := -6^2 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 3^7$	$6355 := -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 5^1$
$5923 := -5^3 - 9^0 - 2^9 + 3^8$	$6247 := 6^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 7^3$	$6356 := -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 6^1$
$5924 := -5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 4^1$	$6249 := -6^3 - 2^5 - 4^3 + 9^4$	$6357 := -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^1$
$5925 := -5^3 + 9^4 - 2^9 + 5^0$	$6249 := 6^4 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 9^3$	$6358 := -6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^1$
		$6359 := -6^3 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 9^4$
		$6362 := -6^3 + 3^8 + 6^0 + 2^4$
		$6373 := -6^3 + 3^3 + 7^0 + 3^8$

$$\begin{aligned} 6379 &:= -6^3 + 3^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\ 6392 &:= -6^3 - 3^4 + 9^4 + 2^7 \\ 6393 &:= -6^1 - 3^4 - 9^2 + 3^8 \\ 6396 &:= -6^4 - 3^1 - 9^2 + 6^5 \\ 6397 &:= -6^3 + 3^1 + 9^4 + 7^2 \\ 6399 &:= -6^3 - 3^3 + 9^2 + 9^4 \\ 6409 &:= -6^3 + 4^3 + 0^1 + 9^4 \\ 6423 &:= -6^1 - 4^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 \\ 6424 &:= 6^4 + 4^5 + 2^3 + 4^6 \\ 6427 &:= -6^1 + 4^6 - 2^6 + 7^4 \\ 6429 &:= -6^2 - 4^3 - 2^5 + 9^4 \\ 6443 &:= 6^4 + 4^5 + 4^6 + 3^3 \\ 6456 &:= -6^4 + 4^0 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\ 6462 &:= -6^4 - 4^2 + 6^5 - 2^1 \\ 6463 &:= -6^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 3^7 \\ 6465 &:= -6^4 - 4^2 + 6^5 + 5^0 \\ 6467 &:= -6^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\ 6468 &:= -6^4 - 4^1 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\ 6483 &:= -6^1 - 4^3 - 8^1 + 3^8 \\ 6487 &:= -6^1 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 7^4 \\ 6490 &:= -6^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 - 0^0 \\ 6492 &:= -6^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 + 2^0 \\ 6506 &:= -6^4 + 5^2 + 0^0 + 6^5 \\ 6519 &:= -6^2 - 5^1 - 1^0 + 9^4 \\ 6523 &:= -6^2 - 5^0 - 2^0 + 3^8 \\ 6529 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 - 2^0 + 9^4 \\ 6530 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 0^1 \\ 6531 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 1^0 \\ 6532 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 2^1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6533 &:= -6^1 + 5^1 - 3^3 + 3^8 \\ 6534 &:= -6^1 - 5^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 \\ 6535 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 5^1 \\ 6536 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 6^1 \\ 6537 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 7^1 \\ 6538 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 \\ 6539 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 3^2 + 9^4 \\ 6549 &:= -6^1 - 5^1 - 4^0 + 9^4 \\ 6553 &:= -6^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 3^8 \\ 6557 &:= -6^2 + 5^5 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\ 6559 &:= -6^1 - 5^0 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\ 6569 &:= 6^1 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 9^4 \\ 6573 &:= 6^1 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 3^8 \\ 6573 &:= -6^1 + 5^2 - 7^1 + 3^8 \\ 6579 &:= 6^1 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\ 6579 &:= -6^1 + 5^2 - 7^0 + 9^4 \\ 6592 &:= -6^1 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 2^5 \\ 6593 &:= 6^1 + 5^2 + 9^0 + 3^8 \\ 6593 &:= -6^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 3^5 \\ 6594 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 9^4 + 4^3 \\ 6595 &:= -6^3 + 5^3 + 9^4 + 5^3 \\ 6596 &:= -6^1 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 6^2 \\ 6599 &:= -6^1 + 5^3 - 9^2 + 9^4 \\ 6599 &:= 6^2 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 9^4 \\ 6603 &:= 6^1 + 6^2 + 0^1 + 3^8 \\ 6605 &:= -6^4 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 5^3 \\ 6623 &:= -6^1 + 6^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 \\ 6624 &:= -6^4 + 6^5 + 2^7 + 4^2 \\ 6632 &:= 6^1 + 6^0 + 3^8 + 2^6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6634 &:= 6^2 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 4^0 \\ 6649 &:= 6^2 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\ 6669 &:= 6^2 + 6^2 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\ 6689 &:= 6^4 + 6^4 + 8^4 + 9^0 \\ 6714 &:= 6^3 + 7^4 + 1^0 + 4^6 \\ 6732 &:= -6^1 + 7^2 + 3^8 + 2^7 \\ 6732 &:= 6^2 + 7^1 + 3^8 + 2^7 \\ 6734 &:= -6^1 + 7^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 \\ 6737 &:= -6^3 + 7^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 \\ 6739 &:= -6^2 + 7^4 - 3^7 + 9^4 \\ 6773 &:= -6^3 + 7^4 + 7^4 + 3^7 \\ 6779 &:= 6^3 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 9^4 \\ 6792 &:= 6^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 + 2^3 \\ 6793 &:= 6^3 + 7^1 + 9^1 + 3^8 \\ 6794 &:= -6^2 + 7^3 - 9^5 + 4^8 \\ 6794 &:= 6^3 + 7^0 + 9^4 + 4^2 \\ 6825 &:= -6^5 - 8^3 - 2^9 + 5^6 \\ 6849 &:= 6^3 + 8^1 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\ 6863 &:= -6^3 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 3^8 \\ 6888 &:= -6^4 - 8^1 + 8^4 + 8^4 \\ 6897 &:= -6^1 - 8^0 + 9^4 + 7^3 \\ 6932 &:= 6^3 + 9^4 + 3^3 + 2^7 \\ 6934 &:= 6^2 + 9^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 \\ 6935 &:= 6^1 + 9^4 + 3^5 + 5^3 \\ 6937 &:= 6^1 + 9^4 + 3^3 + 7^3 \\ 6937 &:= -6^4 - 9^3 + 3^8 + 7^4 \\ 6938 &:= -6^3 + 9^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 \\ 6939 &:= 6^3 + 9^2 + 3^4 + 9^4 \\ 6954 &:= -6^1 + 9^4 - 5^4 + 4^5 \\ 6956 &:= -6^3 - 9^3 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\ 6972 &:= 6^2 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 2^5 \\ 6974 &:= 6^1 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 4^3 \end{aligned}$$

$6976 := 6^2 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 6^2$	$7435 := -7^1 + 4^4 + 3^8 + 5^4$	$7848 := -7^3 - 8^0 + 4^6 + 8^4$
$6979 := -6^1 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^4$	$7436 := -7^3 + 4^1 - 3^0 + 6^5$	$7854 := -7^3 + 8^4 + 5^1 + 4^6$
$6993 := -6^3 - 9^2 + 9^3 + 3^8$	$7453 := -7^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 3^8$	$7893 := -7^3 - 8^3 + 9^4 + 3^7$
$7023 := -7^2 - 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8$	$7496 := -7^3 + 4^3 - 9^0 + 6^5$	$7906 := 7^2 + 9^2 + 0^1 + 6^5$
$7032 := 7^3 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 2^7$	$7526 := -7^3 + 5^3 - 2^5 + 6^5$	$7928 := 7^3 + 9^4 + 2^9 + 8^3$
$7123 := 7^2 + 1^0 + 2^9 + 3^8$	$7530 := 7^3 + 5^4 + 3^8 + 0^0$	$7944 := 7^3 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 4^5$
$7216 := -7^2 - 2^9 + 1^0 + 6^5$	$7562 := -7^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 2^7$	$7962 := 7^2 + 9^1 + 6^5 + 2^7$
$7233 := -7^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 3^8$	$7563 := -7^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 3^4$	$7964 := 7^3 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 4^5$
$7234 := -7^3 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5$	$7564 := -7^3 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 4^4$	$7986 := -7^1 + 9^3 - 8^3 + 6^5$
$7234 := 7^4 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^6$	$7566 := -7^2 - 5^3 - 6^2 + 6^5$	$8194 := 8^4 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 4^6$
$7239 := -7^2 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 9^4$	$7632 := 7^3 + 6^3 + 3^8 + 2^9$	$8208 := 8^4 + 2^4 + 0^1 + 8^4$
$7243 := -7^3 + 2^0 + 4^5 + 3^8$	$7635 := -7^4 - 6^5 + 3^7 + 5^6$	$8224 := 8^4 + 2^4 + 2^4 + 4^6$
$7253 := -7^4 - 2^5 + 5^5 + 3^8$	$7639 := 7^3 + 6^1 + 3^6 + 9^4$	$8226 := -8^2 + 2^1 + 2^9 + 6^5$
$7256 := -7^1 - 2^9 - 5^0 + 6^5$	$7652 := -7^1 + 6^5 - 5^3 + 2^3$	$8228 := 8^4 + 2^2 + 2^5 + 8^4$
$7279 := 7^3 + 2^5 + 7^3 + 9^4$	$7653 := -7^1 + 6^5 - 5^3 + 3^2$	$8245 := 8^3 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^5$
$7294 := -7^4 - 2^7 - 9^4 + 4^7$	$7662 := -7^2 - 6^0 + 6^5 - 2^6$	$8248 := -8^1 + 2^6 + 4^6 + 8^4$
$7296 := -7^1 + 2^8 - 9^3 + 6^5$	$7679 := -7^2 + 6^5 - 7^2 + 9^0$	$8265 := -8^1 - 2^7 + 6^5 + 5^4$
$7296 := 7^1 + 2^9 + 9^4 + 6^3$	$7692 := -7^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 + 2^2$	$8283 := 8^4 + 2^6 + 8^4 + 3^3$
$7299 := 7^1 + 2^1 + 9^3 + 9^4$	$7726 := -7^2 + 7^0 - 2^1 + 6^5$	$8288 := 8^2 + 2^5 + 8^4 + 8^4$
$7299 := -7^1 + 2^4 + 9^3 + 9^4$	$7746 := -7^1 - 7^1 - 4^2 + 6^5$	$8289 := 8^4 + 2^4 + 8^4 + 9^2$
$7322 := -7^1 + 3^8 + 2^8 + 2^9$	$7761 := -7^1 - 7^1 + 6^5 - 1^0$	$8296 := -8^4 - 2^0 + 9^5 - 6^6$
$7323 := 7^1 + 3^5 + 2^9 + 3^8$	$7763 := -7^1 - 7^1 + 6^5 + 3^0$	$8316 := 8^3 + 3^3 + 1^0 + 6^5$
$7329 := 7^1 + 3^6 + 2^5 + 9^4$	$7764 := -7^1 - 7^0 + 6^5 - 4^1$	$8337 := -8^4 - 3^7 - 3^7 + 7^5$
$7343 := 7^2 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 3^8$	$7767 := -7^1 - 7^0 + 6^5 - 7^0$	$8376 := 8^3 + 3^4 + 7^1 + 6^5$
$7363 := 7^3 + 3^5 + 6^3 + 3^8$	$7769 := -7^1 - 7^0 + 6^5 + 9^0$	$8396 := 8^3 + 3^3 + 9^2 + 6^5$
$7368 := -7^3 - 3^0 + 6^5 - 8^2$	$7786 := -7^1 + 7^4 + 8^4 + 6^4$	$8436 := 8^4 + 4^6 + 3^5 + 6^0$
$7416 := -7^3 - 4^2 - 1^0 + 6^5$	$7836 := -7^1 + 8^2 + 3^1 + 6^5$	$8443 := 8^1 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 3^5$
$7426 := -7^3 + 4^0 - 2^3 + 6^5$	$7836 := 7^2 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 6^5$	$8449 := 8^4 + 4^4 + 4^6 + 9^0$
$7432 := 7^3 + 4^2 + 3^8 + 2^9$	$7837 := -7^4 - 8^1 - 3^8 + 7^5$	$8485 := -8^1 - 4^8 - 8^4 + 5^7$
		$8496 := -8^1 - 4^0 + 9^3 + 6^5$
		$8536 := 8^3 + 5^1 + 3^5 + 6^5$
		$8647 := 8^3 + 6^5 + 4^2 + 7^3$

$8667 := 8^3 + 6^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$9236 := 9^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^5$	$9657 := -9^4 + 6^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$8733 := -8^1 - 7^1 + 3^7 + 3^8$	$9236 := -9^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 6^5$	$9679 := -9^2 - 6^5 + 7^5 + 9^3$
$8739 := -8^1 - 7^0 + 3^7 + 9^4$	$9237 := 9^4 + 2^5 + 3^5 + 7^4$	$9693 := 9^3 + 6^3 + 9^4 + 3^7$
$8756 := 8^3 + 7^3 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$9324 := 9^4 + 3^7 + 2^9 + 4^3$	$9697 := 9^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 + 7^4$
$8825 := 8^4 + 8^4 + 2^3 + 5^4$	$9324 := -9^4 - 3^5 - 2^8 + 4^7$	$9723 := 9^3 + 7^4 + 2^5 + 3^8$
$8864 := 8^3 + 8^3 + 6^5 + 4^3$	$9347 := 9^4 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^3$	$9725 := 9^4 + 7^1 + 2^5 + 5^5$
$8897 := -8^2 - 8^0 + 9^4 + 7^4$	$9362 := 9^3 + 3^6 + 6^5 + 2^7$	$9727 := -9^4 - 7^1 - 2^9 + 7^5$
$8970 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 0^1$	$9362 := -9^3 + 3^7 + 6^5 + 2^7$	$9742 := -9^4 - 7^2 + 4^7 - 2^5$
$8971 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 1^0$	$9364 := -9^4 - 3^5 - 6^3 + 4^7$	$9745 := -9^4 - 7^3 + 4^5 + 5^6$
$8972 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 2^1$	$9367 := -9^2 - 3^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$9814 := -9^4 - 8^1 - 1^0 + 4^7$
$8973 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 3^1$	$9385 := 9^4 + 3^7 + 8^3 + 5^3$	$9824 := -9^4 - 8^0 + 2^1 + 4^7$
$8974 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 4^1$	$9437 := -9^3 + 4^7 - 3^8 + 7^3$	$9834 := -9^4 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 4^7$
$8975 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 5^1$	$9454 := -9^4 + 4^4 - 5^4 + 4^7$	$9879 := -9^3 + 8^4 - 7^2 + 9^4$
$8976 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 6^1$	$9455 := -9^1 - 4^8 - 5^5 + 5^7$	$9904 := -9^4 + 9^2 + 0^1 + 4^7$
$8977 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^1 + 7^4$	$9474 := 9^4 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 4^4$	$9924 := -9^3 + 9^4 - 2^2 + 4^6$
$8978 := 8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 8^1$	$9478 := 9^4 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3$	$9942 := -9^1 - 9^4 + 4^7 + 2^7$
$8979 := 8^1 + 9^1 + 7^4 + 9^4$	$9478 := -9^4 - 4^4 + 7^5 - 8^3$	$9944 := -9^3 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 4^6$
$8979 := -8^2 + 9^2 + 7^4 + 9^4$	$9493 := 9^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 + 3^7$	$9947 := 9^3 + 9^4 + 4^4 + 7^4$
$9027 := 9^4 + 0^0 + 2^6 + 7^4$	$9542 := -9^4 - 5^2 + 4^7 - 2^8$	$9963 := -9^1 + 9^1 + 6^5 + 3^7$
$9057 := -9^4 + 0^1 + 5^6 - 7^1$	$9569 := -9^2 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 9^4$	$9963 := 9^3 + 9^3 + 6^5 + 3^6$
$9065 := -9^4 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 5^6$	$9634 := -9^4 - 6^3 + 3^3 + 4^7$	$9964 := -9^3 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 4^6$
$9094 := -9^3 + 0^1 - 9^4 + 4^7$	$9654 := 9^3 + 6^5 + 5^3 + 4^5$	

2.5 Four Digits Numbers

$10176 := -1^1 - 0^0 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 6^5$	$10694 := 1^1 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 9^4 + 4^6$	$11554 := -1^1 + 1^0 + 5^2 + 5^6 - 4^6$
$10237 := -1^1 + 0^1 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 7^5$	$10846 := -1^1 - 0^0 + 8^4 - 4^5 + 6^5$	$11578 := -1^1 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 7^2 - 8^4$
$10372 := -1^1 - 0^0 - 3^8 + 7^5 + 2^7$	$10933 := -1^1 - 0^0 + 9^4 + 3^7 + 3^7$	$11862 := -1^1 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 2^3$
$10649 := -1^1 - 0^0 - 6^1 + 4^6 + 9^4$	$10973 := -1^1 - 0^0 + 9^3 + 7^5 - 3^8$	$11863 := -1^1 + 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 3^2$
$10687 := -1^1 - 0^0 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 7^4$	$11528 := -1^1 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 2^0 - 8^4$	$11864 := -1^1 + 1^0 - 8^1 + 6^5 + 4^6$
$10693 := 1^1 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 + 3^7$	$11538 := -1^1 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 3^2 - 8^4$	$11865 := -1^1 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 5^1$

$11866 := -1^1 + 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 6^1$	$12647 := -1^1 - 2^6 + 6^0 - 4^6 + 7^5$	$13058 := -1^1 - 3^9 - 0^0 - 5^2 + 8^5$
$11869 := -1^1 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 9^0$	$12649 := -1^1 + 2^0 - 6^6 + 4^4 + 9^5$	$13073 := -1^1 - 3^8 + 0^0 - 7^2 + 3^9$
$12284 := -1^1 - 2^0 - 2^1 - 8^4 + 4^7$	$12653 := -1^1 + 2^9 - 6^4 + 5^6 - 3^7$	$13078 := -1^1 - 3^9 + 0^0 - 7^1 + 8^5$
$12296 := -1^1 - 2^5 - 2^6 + 9^5 - 6^6$	$12675 := -1^1 - 2^9 - 6^2 - 7^4 + 5^6$	$13082 := -1^1 - 3^9 - 0^0 + 8^5 - 2^0$
$12348 := -1^1 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 8^4$	$12678 := -1^1 + 2^2 - 6^2 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$13083 := -1^1 - 3^0 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 3^9$
$12367 := 1^1 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$12697 := -1^1 + 2^8 - 6^6 + 9^5 + 7^2$	$13084 := -1^1 - 3^9 + 0^0 + 8^5 - 4^0$
$12367 := -1^1 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$12708 := -1^1 - 2^0 + 7^5 - 0^0 - 8^4$	$13085 := -1^1 - 3^9 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 5^0$
$12369 := -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12724 := -1^1 - 2^1 + 7^5 + 2^4 - 4^6$	$13086 := -1^1 - 3^9 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 6^0$
$12386 := 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 8^4 + 6^5$	$12728 := -1^1 + 2^1 + 7^5 + 2^4 - 8^4$	$13093 := -1^1 - 3^3 - 0^0 + 9^4 + 3^8$
$12386 := -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 8^3 - 6^5$	$12738 := -1^1 + 2^0 + 7^5 + 3^3 - 8^4$	$13095 := -1^1 + 3^8 - 0^0 + 9^4 - 5^2$
$12393 := -1^1 + 2^0 - 3^6 + 9^4 + 3^8$	$12742 := -1^1 - 2^5 + 7^5 - 4^6 + 2^6$	$13123 := -1^1 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 3^8$
$12396 := -1^1 + 2^0 + 3^1 + 9^5 - 6^6$	$12745 := -1^1 - 2^9 - 7^0 + 4^7 - 5^5$	$13132 := 1^1 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 2^3$
$12435 := -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 3^8 + 5^5$	$12783 := -1^1 - 2^3 + 7^5 - 8^4 + 3^4$	$13133 := 1^1 + 3^2 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 3^8$
$12452 := -1^1 - 2^3 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 2^7$	$12789 := -1^1 - 2^1 + 7^5 - 8^4 + 9^2$	$13158 := -1^1 - 3^8 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 8^4$
$12453 := -1^1 - 2^3 - 4^6 - 5^5 + 3^9$	$12832 := -1^1 - 2^8 + 8^5 - 3^9 + 2^2$	$13173 := 1^1 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 7^2 + 3^8$
$12455 := -1^1 - 2^3 - 4^8 - 5^3 + 5^7$	$12833 := -1^1 - 2^3 + 8^5 - 3^5 - 3^9$	$13194 := -1^1 + 3^9 - 1^0 + 9^5 - 4^8$
$12456 := -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^6 - 6^5$	$12836 := -1^1 - 2^5 + 8^5 - 3^9 - 6^3$	$13228 := -1^1 - 3^9 + 2^4 + 2^7 + 8^5$
$12457 := -1^1 - 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$12839 := -1^1 - 2^2 + 8^4 + 3^7 + 9^4$	$13245 := -1^1 + 3^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5$
$12459 := -1^1 - 2^7 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 9^0$	$12853 := -1^1 - 2^8 + 8^5 + 5^2 - 3^9$	$13249 := -1^1 + 3^8 + 2^6 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$12475 := -1^1 - 2^6 - 4^8 - 7^2 + 5^7$	$12856 := -1^1 + 2^5 - 8^4 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$13254 := -1^1 - 3^1 - 2^0 - 5^5 + 4^7$
$12479 := -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^4$	$12864 := -1^1 + 2^0 - 8^5 + 6^6 - 4^5$	$13266 := -1^1 + 3^9 + 2^6 + 6^4 - 6^5$
$12524 := -1^1 - 2^5 + 5^7 - 2^5 - 4^8$	$12896 := -1^1 - 2^3 + 8^3 + 9^5 - 6^6$	$13268 := -1^1 - 3^9 - 2^5 + 6^3 + 8^5$
$12544 := -1^1 - 2^3 + 5^6 + 4^5 - 4^6$	$12929 := -1^1 - 2^6 + 9^4 - 2^7 + 9^4$	$13286 := -1^1 - 3^6 + 2^7 - 8^5 + 6^6$
$12548 := -1^1 - 2^2 + 5^6 + 4^5 - 8^4$	$12945 := -1^1 - 2^1 - 9^4 + 4^7 + 5^5$	$13328 := -1^1 + 3^5 - 3^9 + 2^0 + 8^5$
$12568 := -1^1 - 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^4$	$12984 := -1^1 - 2^5 + 9^3 - 8^4 + 4^7$	$13332 := 1^1 + 3^4 + 3^8 + 3^8 + 2^7$
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$12633 := -1^1 - 2^1 - 6^5 + 3^6 + 3^9$	$12994 := -1^1 - 2^7 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 4^0$	$13336 := -1^1 - 3^0 + 3^8 + 3^8 + 6^3$
$12634 := 1^1 + 2^5 + 6^5 + 3^6 + 4^6$	$12995 := -1^1 - 2^0 + 9^4 + 9^4 - 5^3$	$13337 := 1^1 + 3^7 + 3^7 + 3^8 + 7^4$
$12639 := -1^1 + 2^2 - 6^5 + 3^9 + 9^3$	$13039 := -1^1 - 3^4 - 0^0 + 3^8 + 9^4$	$13338 := -1^1 + 3^6 + 3^8 + 3^8 - 8^3$

$13356 := -1^1 - 3^5 - 3^6 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$13574 := -1^1 - 3^3 - 5^5 + 7^3 + 4^7$	$13861 := -1^1 - 3^3 - 8^5 + 6^6 + 1^0$
$13357 := -1^1 - 3^4 - 3^5 - 5^5 + 7^5$	$13575 := -1^1 - 3^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 5^5$	$13862 := -1^1 - 3^2 - 8^5 + 6^6 - 2^4$
$13359 := -1^1 + 3^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 9^2$	$13578 := -1^1 + 3^5 + 5^4 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$13863 := -1^1 + 3^1 - 8^5 + 6^6 - 3^3$
$13363 := -1^1 - 3^8 + 3^5 - 6^0 + 3^9$	$13596 := -1^1 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 9^3 - 6^4$	$13864 := -1^1 - 3^3 - 8^5 + 6^6 + 4^1$
$13373 := 1^1 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 3^8$	$13597 := -1^1 - 3^1 - 5^5 - 9^2 + 7^5$	$13865 := -1^1 + 3^1 - 8^5 + 6^6 - 5^2$
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$13398 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 3^9 - 9^0 - 8^4$	$13628 := -1^1 - 3^1 + 6^6 - 2^8 - 8^5$	$13868 := -1^1 - 3^3 + 8^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$
$13425 := -1^1 - 3^7 - 4^1 - 2^3 + 5^6$	$13632 := -1^1 + 3^8 - 6^0 + 3^8 + 2^9$	$13869 := -1^1 - 3^2 - 8^5 + 6^6 - 9^1$
$13428 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 4^7 - 2^8 - 8^3$	$13644 := -1^1 - 3^5 + 6^6 - 4^7 - 4^7$	$13885 := -1^1 - 3^7 - 8^2 + 8^3 + 5^6$
$13435 := -1^1 - 3^0 - 4^0 - 3^7 + 5^6$	$13648 := -1^1 - 3^5 + 6^6 + 4^1 - 8^5$	$13886 := -1^1 - 3^2 + 8^1 - 8^5 + 6^6$
$13443 := 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 4^4 + 3^8$	$13652 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 6^3 + 5^6 - 2^0$	$13933 := 1^1 + 3^4 + 9^3 + 3^8 + 3^8$
$13445 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 5^6$	$13654 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 6^3 + 5^6 + 4^0$	$13958 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 9^1 + 5^6 + 8^3$
$13452 := -1^1 - 3^7 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 2^4$	$13665 := -1^1 + 3^8 - 6^4 + 6^5 + 5^4$	$13974 := -1^1 - 3^2 + 9^0 - 7^4 + 4^7$
$13454 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 4^2$	$13668 := -1^1 - 3^1 - 6^3 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$13978 := 1^1 + 3^8 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 8^3$
$13465 := -1^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 5^5$	$13677 := -1^1 - 3^6 + 6^0 - 7^4 + 7^5$	$14047 := -1^1 + 4^3 + 0^0 + 4^7 - 7^4$
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$13502 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 2^6$	$13753 := -1^1 - 3^2 + 7^5 - 5^5 + 3^4$	$14256 := -1^1 - 4^3 - 2^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$
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$13534 := -1^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$13758 := -1^1 - 3^9 + 7^2 + 5^4 + 8^5$	$14276 := 1^1 + 4^6 + 2^1 + 7^4 + 6^5$
$13535 := -1^1 - 3^3 + 5^3 - 3^7 + 5^6$	$13759 := -1^1 - 3^1 + 7^5 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$14276 := -1^1 + 4^6 + 2^2 + 7^4 + 6^5$
$13537 := -1^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 3^7 + 7^3$	$13795 := -1^1 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 9^4 + 5^4$	$14277 := -1^1 - 4^3 - 2^6 - 7^4 + 7^5$
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$13573 := -1^1 - 3^3 - 5^5 + 7^5 - 3^4$	$13846 := -1^1 - 3^6 - 8^3 + 4^7 - 6^4$	$14324 := -1^1 + 4^3 - 3^7 + 2^6 + 4^7$
	$13860 := -1^1 - 3^3 - 8^5 + 6^6 + 0^1$	$14325 := -1^1 - 4^5 - 3^5 - 2^5 + 5^6$
		$14336 := -1^1 + 4^0 - 3^0 + 3^8 + 6^5$
		$14336 := -1^1 - 4^0 + 3^0 + 3^8 + 6^5$

$14344 := -1^1 - 4^5 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 4^7$	$14592 := -1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 9^1 + 2^0$	$14929 := -1^1 + 4^7 - 9^3 + 2^2 - 9^3$
$14345 := -1^1 - 4^4 + 3^0 - 4^5 + 5^6$	$14598 := -1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 9^0 - 8^0$	$14958 := -1^1 - 4^0 - 9^3 + 5^6 + 8^2$
$14346 := 1^1 + 4^1 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^5$	$14605 := -1^1 - 4^5 + 6^1 - 0^0 + 5^6$	$14965 := -1^1 + 4^1 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 5^4$
$14346 := -1^1 - 4^5 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3$	$14635 := -1^1 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 3^5 + 5^6$	$14968 := -1^1 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 6^3 + 8^4$
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$14362 := 1^1 + 4^2 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 2^3$	$14658 := -1^1 - 4^5 - 6^1 + 5^6 + 8^2$	$15138 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 1^0 + 3^3 - 8^3$
$14363 := 1^1 + 4^2 + 3^2 + 6^5 + 3^8$	$14665 := -1^1 - 4^9 - 6^0 + 6^7 - 5^5$	$15139 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 1^0 + 3^5 - 9^3$
$14365 := -1^1 + 4^1 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 5^2$	$14675 := -1^1 + 4^1 - 6^4 + 7^3 + 5^6$	$15157 := -1^1 - 5^3 + 1^0 + 5^6 - 7^3$
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$14377 := -1^1 - 4^0 - 3^3 - 7^4 + 7^5$	$14697 := 1^1 + 4^2 + 6^5 + 9^4 + 7^3$	$15224 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 2^9 + 2^7 - 4^2$
$14385 := -1^1 + 4^7 - 3^7 + 8^2 + 5^3$	$14705 := -1^1 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 0^1 - 5^5$	$15242 := -1^1 - 5^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 2^9$
$14453 := -1^1 + 4^4 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 3^7$	$14742 := -1^1 - 4^5 + 7^5 - 4^5 - 2^4$	$15243 := -1^1 - 5^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 3^1$
$14456 := -1^1 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$14749 := -1^1 - 4^5 + 7^5 - 4^5 - 9^1$	$15244 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 2^7 + 4^1 - 4^4$
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$14543 := -1^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 4^7 - 3^8$	$14848 := -1^1 - 4^5 + 8^0 + 4^7 - 8^3$	$15263 := -1^1 - 5^5 + 2^1 - 6^4 + 3^9$
$14547 := -1^1 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 4^5 - 7^2$	$14852 := -1^1 - 4^1 - 8^3 + 5^6 - 2^8$	$15264 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 2^9 + 6^3 - 4^3$
$14562 := -1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 2^5$	$14853 := -1^1 - 4^2 - 8^3 + 5^6 - 3^5$	$15275 := -1^1 - 5^1 - 2^0 - 7^3 + 5^6$
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		$15342 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 3^3 + 4^0 - 2^8$
		$15346 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 4^0 - 6^2$
		$15352 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 2^8$

$15353 := -1^1 - 5^0 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 3^5$	$15436 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 4^0 + 3^3 - 6^3$	$15549 := -1^1 + 5^1 + 5^6 + 4^0 - 9^2$
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$15379 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 7^1 - 9^1$	$15505 := -1^1 + 5^1 - 5^3 + 0^0 + 5^6$	$15572 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 7^2 - 2^1$
$15381 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 8^0 - 1^0$	$15506 := -1^1 - 5^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 6^1$	$15573 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 7^2 - 3^0$
$15383 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 8^0 - 3^5$	$15507 := -1^1 - 5^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 7^1$	$15574 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 5^6 - 7^2 + 4^1$
$15388 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 8^1 - 8^0$	$15508 := -1^1 - 5^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 8^1$	$15575 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 5^0 - 7^2 + 5^6$
$15390 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 0^1$	$15509 := -1^1 - 5^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 9^1$	$15576 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 5^6 - 7^1 - 6^2$
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$15394 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 4^1$	$15522 := -1^1 + 5^2 + 5^6 + 2^0 - 2^7$	$15582 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 8^0 - 2^4$
$15395 := -1^1 + 5^1 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 5^6$	$15525 := -1^1 + 5^2 - 5^3 + 2^0 + 5^6$	$15584 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 + 8^0 - 4^2$
$15396 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 6^1$	$15532 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 3^3 - 2^6$	$15586 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 8^0 - 6^2$
$15397 := -1^1 - 5^3 + 3^8 + 9^4 + 7^4$	$15533 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 3^2 - 3^4$	$15589 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 8^0 - 9^1$
$15398 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 8^1$	$15534 := -1^1 + 5^0 - 5^5 + 3^9 - 4^5$	$15590 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 9^1 + 0^1$
$15399 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 9^1$	$15536 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 3^4 - 6^1$	$15591 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 9^1 + 1^0$
$15423 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 4^2 + 2^9 - 3^6$	$15537 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 5^6 - 3^4 - 7^0$	$15592 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 + 9^0 - 2^5$
$15424 := -1^1 + 5^0 - 4^5 + 2^6 + 4^7$	$15538 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 + 3^1 - 8^2$	$15593 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 - 3^3$
$15425 := -1^1 + 5^2 - 4^4 + 2^5 + 5^6$	$15539 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 - 3^1 - 9^2$	$15594 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 5^6 - 9^1 - 4^2$
$15426 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 4^2 + 2^1 - 6^3$	$15543 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 + 4^0 - 3^4$	$15595 := -1^1 - 5^1 - 5^2 + 9^0 + 5^6$
$15428 := -1^1 + 5^5 + 4^7 + 2^4 - 8^4$	$15547 := -1^1 - 5^3 + 5^6 - 4^0 + 7^2$	$15596 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 5^6 + 9^1 - 6^2$
		$15597 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 9^0 - 7^0$
		$15598 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 9^1 + 8^1$
		$15599 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 5^6 - 9^0 + 9^0$

$15602 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 0^1 - 2^4$	$15634 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 3^3 - 4^2$	$15658 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 6^2 + 5^6 - 8^0$
$15603 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 0^1 - 3^3$	$15635 := -1^1 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 3^2 + 5^6$	$15659 := -1^1 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 9^1$
$15604 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 0^1 + 4^2$	$15635 := 1^1 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 5^6$	$15660 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 6^2 - 0^0$
$15605 := -1^1 - 5^2 + 6^1 + 0^1 + 5^6$	$15636 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 6^1$	$15660 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 6^2 + 0^0$
$15609 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 0^1 - 9^1$	$15637 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 7^1$	$15662 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 6^2 + 2^0$
$15617 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 1^0 - 7^1$	$15638 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 8^1$	$15663 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 3^3$
$15618 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 1^0 - 8^1$	$15638 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 3^2 - 8^0$	$15664 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 6^2 + 4^0$
$15620 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 2^0 + 0^0$	$15639 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 9^1$	$15665 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 5^6$
$15621 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 2^1 + 1^0$	$15640 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 4^2 - 0^0$	$15667 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 7^0$
$15622 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 2^0 - 2^1$	$15640 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 4^2 + 0^0$	$15668 := -1^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 6^5 - 8^1$
$15623 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 2^0 - 3^0$	$15642 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 2^4$	$15669 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 9^0$
$15624 := -1^1 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 2^9 + 4^7$	$15643 := -1^1 - 5^1 - 6^1 + 4^7 - 3^6$	$15670 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 0^0$
$15625 := -1^1 + 5^0 - 6^0 + 2^0 + 5^6$	$15644 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 4^2$	$15671 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^2 - 1^0$
$15625 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 5^6$	$15645 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 5^6$	$15672 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^2 - 2^1$
$15626 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 2^1 - 6^0$	$15646 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 4^3 - 6^2$	$15673 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^2 - 3^0$
$15626 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 2^1 + 6^0$	$15647 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 7^0$	$15673 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^2 + 3^0$
$15627 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 7^0$	$15648 := -1^1 + 5^4 - 6^4 + 4^7 - 8^2$	$15675 := -1^1 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 7^2 + 5^6$
$15628 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 8^0$	$15649 := -1^1 + 5^0 - 6^1 + 4^7 - 9^3$	$15677 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 7^2$
$15629 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 9^0$	$15649 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 9^0$	$15678 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 - 8^0$
$15629 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 2^1 + 9^1$	$15650 := -1^1 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 0^1$	$15681 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 - 1^0$
$15630 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 0^1$	$15651 := -1^1 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 1^0$	$15683 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 + 3^0$
$15630 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 3^0 - 0^0$	$15652 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 2^5$	$15684 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 4^2$
$15631 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 1^0$	$15653 := -1^1 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 3^3$	$15686 := 1^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 + 6^5$
$15631 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 3^2 - 1^0$	$15653 := 1^1 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 3^0$	$15686 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^2 - 6^0$
$15632 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 2^2$	$15654 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 6^2 + 5^6 - 4^0$	$15687 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 7^2$
$15632 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 2^3$	$15655 := -1^1 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 5^2 + 5^6$	$15688 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^0 + 8^2$
$15633 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 3^1$	$15656 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$15692 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 2^6$
$15633 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 3^2$	$15657 := -1^1 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 7^1$	$15697 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^2 - 7^1$
$15634 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 4^1$	$15658 := 1^1 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 5^6 + 8^0$	$15698 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 8^2$
		$15703 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 7^2 + 0^0 + 3^3$
		$15709 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 9^2$
		$15712 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^3 + 1^0 - 2^8$

$15713 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 3^4$	$15824 := -1^1 - 5^4 + 8^2 + 2^1 + 4^7$	$15955 := -1^1 + 5^1 - 9^5 + 5^7 - 5^5$
$15732 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 7^1 + 3^5 - 2^7$	$15827 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 8^5 - 2^7 - 7^5$	$15956 := -1^1 + 5^3 - 9^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$15733 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^0 + 3^3 + 3^4$	$15832 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 8^0 + 3^4 + 2^7$	$15957 := -1^1 - 5^0 - 9^1 + 5^6 + 7^3$
$15735 := -1^1 - 5^3 - 7^1 + 3^5 + 5^6$	$15842 := -1^1 - 5^2 - 8^3 + 4^7 - 2^2$	$15958 := -1^1 - 5^5 - 9^5 + 5^7 + 8^1$
$15736 := -1^1 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 3^6 - 6^3$	$15843 := -1^1 - 5^0 - 8^3 + 4^7 - 3^3$	$15959 := -1^1 - 5^5 + 9^1 + 5^7 - 9^5$
$15738 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 8^2$	$15845 := -1^1 - 5^0 - 8^3 + 4^7 - 5^2$	$15962 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 9^2 + 6^0 + 2^8$
$15739 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 3^3 + 9^2$	$15846 := -1^1 - 5^6 - 8^5 + 4^8 - 6^4$	$15964 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 9^2 + 6^0 + 4^4$
$15740 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 7^2 + 4^3 + 0^0$	$15847 := -1^1 - 5^2 - 8^3 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$15967 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 9^0 + 6^0 + 7^3$
$15750 := -1^1 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 5^6 + 0^1$	$15854 := -1^1 - 5^2 - 8^0 + 5^6 + 4^4$	$15970 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 0^1$
$15751 := -1^1 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 5^6 + 1^0$	$15862 := -1^1 - 5^6 + 8^5 - 6^4 + 2^4$	$15971 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 1^0$
$15752 := -1^1 + 5^0 - 7^0 + 5^6 + 2^7$	$15864 := -1^1 - 5^0 - 8^3 - 6^1 + 4^7$	$15972 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 2^1$
$15753 := 1^1 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 5^6 + 3^0$	$15873 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 8^0 + 7^1 + 3^5$	$15972 := -1^1 - 5^4 - 9^2 + 7^5 - 2^7$
$15753 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 7^2 + 5^6 + 3^4$	$15882 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 2^8$	$15973 := -1^1 + 5^4 - 9^3 + 7^5 - 3^6$
$15754 := -1^1 - 5^1 + 7^0 - 5^4 + 4^7$	$15882 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 8^2 + 8^2 + 2^7$	$15973 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 3^1$
$15755 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 7^1 + 5^3 + 5^6$	$15883 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 3^5$	$15974 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 4^1$
$15756 := -1^1 + 5^1 + 7^3 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15884 := -1^1 + 5^1 - 8^3 + 8^1 + 4^7$	$15974 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 9^1 + 7^3 + 4^2$
$15757 := -1^1 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 5^6 + 7^1$	$15884 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 4^4$	$15975 := 1^1 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 5^6$
$15758 := -1^1 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 5^6 + 8^1$	$15892 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 2^8$	$15975 := -1^1 - 5^0 + 9^1 + 7^3 + 5^6$
$15759 := -1^1 + 5^1 + 7^2 + 5^6 + 9^2$	$15932 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 2^6$	$15976 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 6^1$
$15759 := 1^1 + 5^3 + 7^1 + 5^6 + 9^0$	$15933 := -1^1 + 5^4 + 9^4 + 3^7 + 3^8$	$15977 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^1 + 7^3$
$15762 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 2^7$	$15934 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 4^3$	$15977 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 9^1 + 7^0 + 7^3$
$15764 := -1^1 - 5^4 + 7^1 - 6^0 + 4^7$	$15934 := -1^1 - 5^3 - 9^2 - 3^5 + 4^7$	$15978 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 8^1$
$15773 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^2 + 7^3 - 3^5$	$15937 := -1^1 - 5^4 - 9^0 - 3^5 + 7^5$	$15979 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 9^1$
$15774 := -1^1 - 5^0 - 7^1 + 7^5 - 4^5$	$15939 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 9^1 + 3^5 + 9^2$	$16047 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 0^0 + 4^7 - 7^3$
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$15792 := -1^1 + 5^6 - 7^2 + 9^3 - 2^9$	$15951 := -1^1 - 5^5 - 9^5 + 5^7 + 1^0$	$16062 := -1^1 + 6^5 - 0^0 + 6^5 + 2^9$
$15793 := -1^1 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 9^2 + 3^4$	$15952 := -1^1 - 5^5 - 9^5 + 5^7 + 2^1$	$16078 := -1^1 - 6^3 + 0^1 + 7^5 - 8^3$
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$15822 := 1^1 + 5^6 + 8^2 + 2^2 + 2^7$	$15954 := -1^1 + 5^4 + 9^3 + 5^6 - 4^5$	$16234 := -1^1 - 6^2 - 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^7$
		$16237 := -1^1 - 6^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 7^5$
		$16247 := -1^1 - 6^0 - 2^7 + 4^7 - 7^1$
		$16248 := -1^1 + 6^0 - 2^7 + 4^7 - 8^1$

$16249 := -1^1 - 6^3 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 9^2$	$16349 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 9^0$	$16424 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^0 + 2^2 + 4^7$
$16253 := -1^1 - 6^2 - 2^6 + 5^6 + 3^6$	$16351 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 3^6 + 5^6 - 1^0$	$16425 := -1^1 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 5^2$
$16254 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 2^1 - 5^3 + 4^7$	$16352 := -1^1 + 6^0 + 3^6 + 5^6 - 2^1$	$16426 := 1^1 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^2 + 6^2$
$16255 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 2^9 + 5^3 + 5^6$	$16353 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 3^6$	$16426 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 6^2$
$16257 := -1^1 - 6^2 - 2^9 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$16354 := -1^1 - 6^0 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 4^7$	$16427 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 - 2^2 + 7^2$
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$16272 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 2^4 + 7^5 - 2^9$	$16357 := 1^1 + 6^0 + 3^6 + 5^6 + 7^0$	$16429 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^7 - 9^2$
$16273 := -1^1 + 6^1 - 2^9 + 7^5 - 3^3$	$16358 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 3^6 + 5^6 - 8^0$	$16430 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 0^1$
$16274 := -1^1 - 6^2 - 2^9 + 7^5 + 4^2$	$16359 := 1^1 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 9^3$	$16431 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 1^0$
$16275 := -1^1 + 6^1 - 2^9 + 7^5 - 5^2$	$16363 := 1^1 + 6^4 + 3^6 + 6^5 + 3^8$	$16432 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 2^5$
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$16284 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 2^0 - 8^2 + 4^7$	$16384 := -1^1 + 6^0 - 3^0 + 8^0 + 4^7$	$16434 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 3^3 + 4^7$
$16287 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 2^0 - 8^3 + 7^5$	$16384 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 4^7$	$16435 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 5^1$
$16294 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 2^1 - 9^2 + 4^7$	$16385 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 3^5 + 8^3 + 5^6$	$16435 := -1^1 - 6^3 + 4^5 + 3^1 + 5^6$
$16295 := -1^1 + 6^1 - 2^6 + 9^3 + 5^6$	$16394 := -1^1 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 9^1 + 4^7$	$16436 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 6^2$
$16296 := -1^1 + 6^5 + 2^4 + 9^3 + 6^5$	$16402 := 1^1 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 0^1 + 2^4$	$16437 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 7^1$
$16297 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 2^9 + 9^1 + 7^5$	$16403 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 4^7 - 0^0 + 3^3$	$16438 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 8^1$
$16304 := -1^1 + 6^0 - 3^4 + 0^0 + 4^7$	$16404 := -1^1 + 6^2 - 4^2 + 0^0 + 4^7$	$16438 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 4^7 - 3^1 + 8^2$
$16324 := -1^1 + 6^1 - 3^4 + 2^4 + 4^7$	$16412 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 1^0 - 2^3$	$16439 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 9^1$
$16325 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 3^6 + 2^3 + 5^6$	$16415 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 5^2$	$16440 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 4^3 + 4^7 - 0^0$
$16327 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 3^6 + 2^8 + 7^5$	$16419 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 1^0 - 9^0$	$16442 := -1^1 - 6^0 - 4^1 + 4^7 + 2^6$
$16342 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 2^5$	$16420 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 2^5 - 0^0$	$16443 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 4^3 + 4^7 - 3^1$
$16343 := -1^1 - 6^2 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 3^1$	$16421 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 2^0 + 1^0$	$16444 := -1^1 + 6^0 - 4^1 + 4^3 + 4^7$
$16344 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 3^0 - 4^1 + 4^7$	$16422 := 1^1 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^2 + 2^5$	$16445 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 4^3 + 4^7 - 5^0$
$16345 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^1$	$16422 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 2^5$	$16447 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 4^2 + 4^7 + 7^2$
$16346 := 1^1 + 6^5 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^5$	$16423 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 2^0 + 3^0$	$16448 := -1^1 + 6^0 - 4^7 + 4^3 + 8^5$
$16347 := -1^1 - 6^2 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$16423 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^5 + 3^2$	$16449 := -1^1 + 6^0 - 4^2 + 4^7 + 9^2$
$16348 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 3^0 - 4^7 + 8^5$	$16424 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 2^5 + 4^7$	$16452 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 2^5$

$16456 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 6^2$	$16499 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 9^2 - 9^0$	$16729 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 - 2^5 - 9^1$
$16458 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 8^2$	$16523 := -1^1 - 6^2 - 5^5 + 2^1 + 3^9$	$16732 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 3^2 - 2^6$
$16459 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 9^2$	$16524 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 5^1 + 2^7 + 4^7$	$16733 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 + 3^2 - 3^4$
$16467 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^2$	$16527 := -1^1 - 6^3 + 5^0 - 2^6 + 7^5$	$16734 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^3 + 3^2 + 4^7$
$16469 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 9^2$	$16534 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 5^3 + 3^3 + 4^7$	$16736 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^4 + 3^8 + 6^5$
$16470 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 0^1$	$16537 := -1^1 - 6^0 - 5^2 - 3^5 + 7^5$	$16738 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 3^1 - 8^2$
$16471 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 1^0$	$16542 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 5^2 + 4^7 + 2^7$	$16740 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 4^3 - 0^0$
$16472 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 2^5$	$16543 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 3^3$	$16742 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 4^7 + 2^3$
$16472 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 2^2$	$16543 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 4^7 - 3^0$	$16742 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 + 4^0 - 2^6$
$16473 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 3^4$	$16545 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 5^0 + 4^7 + 5^3$	$16743 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 4^7 + 3^2$
$16474 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 4^7$	$16547 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$16744 := -1^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 + 4^0 - 4^3$
$16474 := -1^1 - 6^6 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 4^8$	$16548 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 5^6 + 4^5 - 8^2$	$16745 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^3 + 4^7 + 5^2$
$16475 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 5^1$	$16563 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 3^6$	$16747 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 7^2 - 4^1 + 7^5$
$16475 := -1^1 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 5^3$	$16564 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 4^7$	$16753 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 5^2 - 3^3$
$16476 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 6^2$	$16568 := -1^1 + 6^3 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^3$	$16754 := 1^1 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 5^2 + 4^7$
$16477 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 7^2$	$16574 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 4^4$	$16755 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 5^2 - 5^2$
$16477 := -1^1 - 6^3 - 4^3 - 7^2 + 7^5$	$16576 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 5^6 - 7^3 + 6^4$	$16757 := -1^1 - 6^0 - 7^2 + 5^0 + 7^5$
$16478 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^1$	$16587 := -1^1 - 6^3 + 5^1 - 8^1 + 7^5$	$16762 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 6^1 - 2^5$
$16479 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^2$	$16627 := -1^1 + 6^2 - 6^3 + 2^0 + 7^5$	$16763 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 6^2 - 3^0$
$16479 := -1^1 - 6^6 + 4^8 - 7^4 + 9^0$	$16634 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 6^3 + 3^3 + 4^7$	$16765 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 6^2 + 5^0$
$16482 := 1^1 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 8^2 + 2^5$	$16644 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 6^1 + 4^4 + 4^7$	$16768 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 6^2 - 8^0$
$16482 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 8^2 - 2^0$	$16647 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 7^2$	$16770 := -1^1 - 6^2 - 7^0 + 7^5 + 0^0$
$16484 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^0 + 8^2 + 4^7$	$16695 := -1^1 - 6^3 + 6^4 - 9^1 + 5^6$	$16772 := -1^1 - 6^0 - 7^0 + 7^5 - 2^5$
$16486 := 1^1 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 8^2 + 6^2$	$16722 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 7^5 + 2^3 - 2^7$	$16773 := -1^1 + 6^0 - 7^1 + 7^5 - 3^3$
$16489 := -1^1 - 6^6 + 4^0 + 8^4 + 9^5$	$16723 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 2^0 - 3^4$	$16774 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^2 + 7^3 + 4^7$
$16492 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 9^1 + 2^6$	$16724 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^3 - 2^0 + 4^7$	$16775 := -1^1 + 6^0 - 7^1 + 7^5 - 5^2$
$16494 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 4^3 + 9^1 + 4^7$	$16725 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 7^5 + 2^3 - 5^3$	$16776 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^1 + 7^5 - 6^2$
$16495 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 5^2$	$16726 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 - 2^3 - 6^2$	$16778 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 7^1 + 7^5 + 8^0$
$16496 := -1^1 - 6^4 - 4^9 + 9^0 + 6^7$	$16728 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 2^3 - 8^2$	$16782 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 2^2$
		$16783 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 8^1 - 3^2$
		$16784 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^3 + 8^2 + 4^7$
		$16786 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 8^1 - 6^1$

$16790 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 9^1 - 0^0$	$16883 := -1^1 + 6^4 - 8^4 + 8^0 + 3^9$	$17224 := 1^1 + 7^5 + 2^5 + 2^7 + 4^4$
$16792 := -1^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 + 9^0 - 2^4$	$16925 := 1^1 + 6^4 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 5^6$	$17225 := -1^1 + 7^5 + 2^5 + 2^9 - 5^3$
$16793 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 9^1 - 3^1$	$16925 := -1^1 + 6^4 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 5^6$	$17226 := -1^1 + 7^5 + 2^7 + 2^8 + 6^2$
$16795 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 9^1 - 5^0$	$16927 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 9^2 + 2^5 + 7^5$	$17229 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 2^3 + 2^9 - 9^2$
$16797 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^0 - 9^1 + 7^5$	$16927 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 9^0 + 2^7 + 7^5$	$17240 := 1^1 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 0^1$
$16798 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 + 9^0 - 8^1$	$16942 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 4^7 + 2^9$	$17241 := 1^1 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 1^0$
$16799 := -1^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 + 9^0 - 9^1$	$16942 := -1^1 + 6^4 - 9^3 + 4^7 - 2^3$	$17242 := 1^1 + 7^3 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 2^9$
$16807 := -1^1 + 6^0 - 8^0 + 0^0 + 7^5$	$16945 := -1^1 + 6^3 + 9^2 + 4^5 + 5^6$	$17242 := -1^1 + 7^3 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 2^9$
$16807 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 7^5$	$16949 := -1^1 + 6^4 - 9^0 + 4^7 - 9^3$	$17243 := 1^1 + 7^0 + 2^7 + 4^7 + 3^6$
$16827 := -1^1 + 6^1 - 8^0 + 2^4 + 7^5$	$16965 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 6^4 + 5^6$	$17244 := 1^1 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 4^7$
$16834 := -1^1 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 3^5 + 4^7$	$16984 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 9^2 + 8^3 + 4^7$	$17245 := 1^1 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^1$
$16837 := 1^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 7^5$	$16985 := -1^1 + 6^4 + 9^0 + 8^2 + 5^6$	$17246 := 1^1 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^1$
$16837 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 8^2 - 3^3 + 7^5$	$16987 := -1^1 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 8^2 + 7^5$	$17246 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 6^3$
$16843 := -1^1 + 6^3 + 8^0 + 4^7 + 3^5$	$17026 := 1^1 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 6^3$	$17247 := 1^1 + 7^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16847 := -1^1 + 6^0 + 8^3 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$17026 := -1^1 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 2^2 + 6^3$	$17247 := -1^1 - 7^1 + 2^9 - 4^3 + 7^5$
$16852 := -1^1 + 6^4 - 8^2 + 5^6 - 2^2$	$17032 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 3^5 - 2^4$	$17248 := 1^1 + 7^3 + 2^3 + 4^7 + 8^3$
$16853 := -1^1 - 6^3 + 8^3 - 5^5 + 3^9$	$17034 := -1^1 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 3^5 - 4^2$	$17249 := 1^1 + 7^1 + 2^7 + 4^7 + 9^3$
$16854 := -1^1 - 6^2 + 8^3 - 5^1 + 4^7$	$17039 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 3^5 - 9^1$	$17262 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 2^4 + 6^3 + 2^8$
$16855 := -1^1 + 6^4 - 8^2 + 5^6 - 5^0$	$17053 := 1^1 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 3^5$	$17263 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 2^1 + 6^3 + 3^5$
$16857 := 1^1 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$17053 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 5^1 + 3^5$	$17265 := -1^1 + 7^3 + 2^1 + 6^4 + 5^6$
$16857 := -1^1 + 6^4 - 8^2 + 5^6 + 7^0$	$17055 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 5^3 + 5^3$	$17269 := -1^1 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 6^3 - 9^1$
$16859 := -1^1 - 6^1 + 8^3 + 5^6 + 9^3$	$17062 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 2^8$	$17270 := -1^1 - 7^2 + 2^9 + 7^5 + 0^0$
$16870 := -1^1 - 6^0 + 8^2 + 7^5 + 0^0$	$17064 := -1^1 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 4^4$	$17273 := -1^1 - 7^1 - 2^0 - 7^4 + 3^9$
$16872 := -1^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 7^5 + 2^6$	$17072 := 1^1 + 7^1 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 2^8$	$17275 := -1^1 + 7^3 + 2^0 + 7^5 + 5^3$
$16873 := -1^1 - 6^1 - 8^1 + 7^5 + 3^4$	$17086 := -1^1 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 6^3$	$17276 := -1^1 + 7^3 + 2^7 + 7^5 - 6^0$
$16874 := 1^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 7^5 + 4^3$	$17133 := 1^1 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 3^4 + 3^5$	$17278 := -1^1 + 7^3 + 2^7 + 7^5 + 8^0$
$16875 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 8^2 + 7^5 - 5^0$	$17157 := 1^1 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$17282 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 2^2 + 8^3 - 2^5$
$16877 := -1^1 + 6^1 + 8^2 + 7^0 + 7^5$	$17175 := -1^1 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 5^2$	$17283 := -1^1 - 7^4 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 3^9$
$16879 := 1^1 + 6^1 + 8^2 + 7^5 + 9^0$	$17222 := -1^1 + 7^5 + 2^5 + 2^7 + 2^8$	$17285 := -1^1 + 7^5 - 2^3 + 8^3 - 5^2$
		$17286 := -1^1 + 7^5 + 2^2 + 8^3 - 6^2$
		$17287 := -1^1 + 7^0 - 2^5 + 8^3 + 7^5$
		$17287 := 1^1 + 7^3 + 2^7 + 8^1 + 7^5$

$$\begin{aligned} 17293 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 2^0 + 9^3 - 3^5 & 17357 &:= 1^1 + 7^3 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 & 17532 &:= -1^1 - 7^3 + 5^6 + 3^7 + 2^6 \\ 17305 &:= -1^1 - 7^4 + 3^9 - 0^0 + 5^2 & 17358 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 3^2 + 5^4 - 8^2 & 17533 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 5^0 + 3^6 - 3^0 \\ 17312 &:= -1^1 - 7^4 + 3^9 - 1^0 + 2^5 & 17359 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 3^2 + 5^4 - 9^2 & 17534 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 5^1 + 3^6 + 4^1 \\ 17316 &:= -1^1 - 7^4 + 3^9 - 1^0 + 6^2 & 17363 &:= -1^1 - 7^4 + 3^4 + 6^0 + 3^9 & 17535 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 5^0 + 3^6 - 5^0 \\ 17318 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 3^0 + 1^0 + 8^3 & 17372 &:= 1^1 + 7^2 + 3^1 + 7^5 + 2^9 & 17535 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 5^0 + 3^6 + 5^0 \\ 17320 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 3^0 + 2^9 + 0^0 & 17376 &:= 1^1 + 7^3 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 6^3 & 17536 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 5^1 + 3^6 + 6^1 \\ 17322 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 2^9 & 17378 &:= 1^1 + 7^2 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 8^3 & 17537 &:= -1^1 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 3^6 + 7^5 \\ 17322 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 3^1 + 2^0 + 2^9 & 17398 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 3^0 + 9^2 + 8^3 & 17538 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 5^1 + 3^6 + 8^1 \\ 17324 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 4^0 & 17407 &:= 1^1 + 7^3 + 4^4 + 0^1 + 7^5 & 17539 &:= -1^1 + 7^4 + 5^6 + 3^5 - 9^3 \\ 17326 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 3^2 + 2^9 - 6^0 & 17424 &:= -1^1 + 7^0 + 4^5 + 2^4 + 4^7 & 17539 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 9^3 \\ 17328 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 3^2 + 2^0 + 8^3 & 17424 &:= 1^1 + 7^1 + 4^5 + 2^3 + 4^7 & 17543 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 5^1 + 4^0 + 3^6 \\ 17332 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 3^1 + 3^2 + 2^9 & 17435 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 5^4 & 17552 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 5^4 - 2^2 \\ 17332 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 2^8 & 17435 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 5^4 & 17553 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 5^4 - 3^1 \\ 17334 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 & 17442 &:= 1^1 + 7^0 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 2^5 & 17555 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 5^0 + 5^3 + 5^4 \\ 17335 &:= -1^1 + 7^2 + 3^6 + 3^9 - 5^5 & 17443 &:= 1^1 + 7^1 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 3^3 & 17557 &:= -1^1 + 7^0 + 5^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\ 17338 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 3^2 + 3^2 + 8^3 & 17443 &:= 1^1 + 7^1 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 3^3 & 17559 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 5^4 + 9^0 \\ 17344 &:= -1^1 - 7^4 + 3^9 - 4^0 + 4^3 & 17445 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 4^4 + 4^4 + 5^3 & 17559 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 5^0 + 5^2 + 9^3 \\ 17346 &:= -1^1 - 7^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^0 & 17446 &:= 1^1 + 7^0 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 6^2 & 17562 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 5^4 + 6^0 + 2^7 \\ 17348 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 8^3 & 17448 &:= -1^1 + 7^2 + 4^5 + 4^7 - 8^1 & 17563 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 3^6 \\ 17350 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 3^4 + 5^4 + 0^1 & 17448 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 8^3 & 17579 &:= -1^1 + 7^2 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^3 \\ 17351 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 3^4 + 5^4 + 1^0 & 17450 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 0^0 & 17592 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 5^2 + 9^3 + 2^5 \\ 17352 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 3^2 + 5^2 + 2^9 & 17455 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 4^0 + 5^2 + 5^4 & 17593 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 5^4 + 9^2 + 3^4 \\ 17352 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 2^9 & 17463 &:= 1^1 + 7^3 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 3^6 & 17594 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 5^1 + 9^3 + 4^3 \\ 17353 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 3^1 + 5^4 - 3^4 & 17464 &:= 1^1 + 7^2 + 4^5 + 6^1 + 4^7 & 17596 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 5^2 + 9^3 + 6^2 \\ 17354 &:= 1^1 + 7^3 + 3^0 + 5^4 + 4^7 & 17464 &:= -1^1 - 7^3 + 4^2 + 6^7 - 4^9 & 17598 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 5^0 + 9^3 + 8^2 \\ 17354 &:= -1^1 + 7^3 + 3^1 + 5^4 + 4^7 & 17483 &:= 1^1 + 7^3 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 3^5 & 17622 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 6^4 + 2^5 - 2^9 \\ 17355 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 3^4 + 5^1 + 5^4 & 17486 &:= -1^1 - 7^2 - 4^4 - 8^6 + 6^7 & 17629 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 6^4 + 2^8 - 9^3 \\ 17356 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 3^4 + 5^4 + 6^1 & 17513 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 + 5^4 + 1^0 + 3^4 & 17650 &:= 1^1 + 7^5 + 6^3 + 5^4 + 0^0 \\ 17357 &:= -1^1 + 7^1 - 3^4 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17530 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 5^1 + 3^6 + 0^1 & 17659 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 6^0 + 5^3 + 9^3 \\ & & 17531 &:= -1^1 + 7^5 - 5^1 + 3^6 + 1^0 & 17664 &:= -1^1 - 7^3 + 6^3 + 6^7 - 4^9 \\ & & & & 17737 &:= 1^1 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 3^5 + 7^5 \\ & & & & 17760 &:= -1^1 - 7^3 + 7^5 + 6^4 + 0^0 \end{aligned}$$

- 17774** := $-1^1 - 7^1 - 7^2 + 7^5 + 4^5$ **17952** := $-1^1 + 7^4 - 9^1 + 5^6 - 2^6$ **18544** := $-1^1 + 8^3 + 5^4 + 4^5 + 4^7$
17775 := $-1^1 + 7^0 + 7^3 + 7^5 + 5^4$ **17953** := $-1^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 5^6 - 3^4$ **18569** := $-1^1 - 8^3 + 5^7 + 6^1 - 9^5$
17792 := $-1^1 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 2^8$ **17954** := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 9^0 + 5^3 + 4^5$ **18617** := $1^1 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 7^5$
17794 := $1^1 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 4^4$ **17975** := $-1^1 - 7^2 - 9^0 + 7^4 + 5^6$ **18634** := $-1^1 - 8^1 - 6^4 + 3^9 + 4^4$
17822 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 8^1 + 2^9 + 2^9$ **17994** := $1^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 + 9^2 + 4^5$ **18643** := $-1^1 + 8^0 - 6^4 + 4^4 + 3^9$
17824 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 8^1 + 2^1 + 4^5$ **18046** := $-1^1 - 8^6 - 0^0 + 4^4 + 6^7$ **18678** := $-1^1 + 8^2 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 8^3$
17825 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 2^9 - 5^1$ **18167** := $-1^1 + 8^2 + 1^0 + 6^4 + 7^5$ **18697** := $1^1 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 9^2 + 7^5$
17829 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 2^9 - 9^0$ **18274** := $-1^1 - 8^3 + 2^1 + 7^4 + 4^7$ **18723** := $-1^1 + 8^4 + 7^5 + 2^3 - 3^7$
17834 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 4^5$ **18324** := $-1^1 + 8^4 - 3^7 + 2^5 + 4^7$ **18724** := $-1^1 - 8^2 + 7^4 + 2^2 + 4^7$
17834 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 8^0 + 3^1 + 4^5$ **18325** := $-1^1 + 8^3 + 3^7 + 2^1 + 5^6$ **18727** := $-1^1 - 8^3 + 7^4 + 2^5 + 7^5$
17840 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 0^1$ **18326** := $-1^1 - 8^2 + 3^9 + 2^2 - 6^4$ **18745** := $-1^1 - 8^2 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 5^2$
17841 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 1^0$ **18345** := $-1^1 - 8^4 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^6$ **18753** := $-1^1 - 8^0 + 7^4 + 5^6 + 3^6$
17842 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 2^1$ **18346** := $-1^1 - 8^1 + 3^7 + 4^7 - 6^3$ **18755** := $-1^1 - 8^0 + 7^1 + 5^5 + 5^6$
17842 := $-1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 2^2$ **18347** := $1^1 + 8^3 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 7^5$ **18784** := $-1^1 - 8^0 + 7^4 + 8^0 + 4^7$
17843 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 3^1$ **18362** := $-1^1 - 8^1 + 3^9 - 6^4 - 2^4$ **18794** := $-1^1 + 8^0 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^7$
17844 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^1 + 4^5$ **18364** := $-1^1 - 8^3 - 3^1 - 6^6 + 4^8$ **18835** := $-1^1 + 8^3 + 8^3 + 3^7 + 5^6$
17845 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 5^1$ **18365** := $-1^1 + 8^3 + 3^9 + 6^4 - 5^5$ **18847** := $-1^1 - 8^0 + 8^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$
17846 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 6^1$ **18368** := $-1^1 - 8^2 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 8^4$ **18849** := $-1^1 + 8^0 - 8^4 + 4^7 + 9^4$
17846 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 + 4^4 + 6^4$ **18369** := $-1^1 - 8^1 + 3^9 - 6^4 - 9^1$ **18923** := $-1^1 - 8^3 + 9^1 - 2^8 + 3^9$
17847 := $1^1 + 7^1 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 7^5$ **18386** := $-1^1 - 8^0 + 3^9 + 8^0 - 6^4$ **18946** := $1^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 6^5$
17848 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 8^1$ **18396** := $-1^1 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 9^1 - 6^4$ **18953** := $-1^1 - 8^0 - 9^3 + 5^0 + 3^9$
17849 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 9^1$ **18436** := $1^1 + 8^3 + 4^7 + 3^5 + 6^4$ **18963** := $-1^1 - 8^3 + 9^1 - 6^3 + 3^9$
17854 := $-1^1 + 7^5 - 8^0 + 5^2 + 4^5$ **18436** := $-1^1 + 8^4 + 4^1 + 3^8 + 6^5$ **18985** := $-1^1 - 8^4 - 9^4 + 8^5 - 5^5$
17862 := $-1^1 + 7^1 - 8^6 + 6^7 + 2^6$ **18453** := $-1^1 + 8^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 3^5$ **19033** := $-1^1 + 9^2 - 0^0 + 3^9 - 3^6$
17865 := $-1^1 + 7^2 - 8^6 + 6^7 + 5^2$ **18456** := $-1^1 + 8^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$ **19073** := $-1^1 + 9^2 - 0^0 + 7^5 + 3^7$
17868 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 6^2 + 8^3$ **18472** := $1^1 + 8^3 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 2^7$ **19075** := $-1^1 - 9^5 + 0^0 - 7^0 + 5^7$
17879 := $-1^1 + 7^3 + 8^0 + 7^5 + 9^3$ **18496** := $-1^1 + 8^2 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 6^5$ **19075** := $-1^1 - 9^5 - 0^0 + 7^0 + 5^7$
17914 := $1^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 + 1^0 + 4^5$ **18534** := $-1^1 + 8^0 - 5^3 + 3^9 - 4^5$ **19243** := $-1^1 + 9^1 - 2^9 + 4^3 + 3^9$
17945 := $-1^1 + 7^4 - 9^2 + 4^0 + 5^6$ **18539** := $-1^1 - 8^0 + 5^6 + 3^7 + 9^3$ **19332** := $-1^1 + 9^2 + 3^4 + 3^9 - 2^9$
18534 := $-1^1 + 8^0 - 5^3 + 3^9 - 4^5$ **19335** := $-1^1 - 9^3 - 3^5 + 3^9 + 5^4$
18539 := $-1^1 - 8^0 + 5^6 + 3^7 + 9^3$ **19337** := $-1^1 - 9^0 - 3^0 + 3^9 - 7^3$
19344 := $-1^1 - 9^2 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 4^4$

$19346 := -1^1 - 9^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^0$	$19645 := -1^1 - 9^2 + 6^1 + 4^6 + 5^6$	$19845 := -1^1 - 9^1 + 8^4 + 4^7 - 5^4$
$19353 := -1^1 - 9^2 - 3^5 - 5^1 + 3^9$	$19646 := -1^1 - 9^0 + 6^5 + 4^6 + 6^5$	$19862 := -1^1 - 9^5 + 8^5 + 6^6 - 2^9$
$19386 := -1^1 - 9^2 + 3^9 + 8^0 - 6^3$	$19673 := -1^1 - 9^0 - 6^0 - 7^1 + 3^9$	$19863 := -1^1 + 9^2 + 8^2 + 6^2 + 3^9$
$19392 := -1^1 - 9^2 + 3^9 - 9^2 - 2^7$	$19683 := -1^1 + 9^0 - 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^9$	$19933 := -1^1 - 9^0 + 9^1 + 3^5 + 3^9$
$19395 := -1^1 - 9^2 + 3^9 - 9^2 - 5^3$	$19685 := -1^1 + 9^0 - 6^2 + 8^4 + 5^6$	$20053 := -2^8 + 0^0 + 0^1 + 5^4 + 3^9$
$19423 := -1^1 - 9^0 - 4^4 - 2^1 + 3^9$	$19687 := -1^1 + 9^2 - 6^4 + 8^4 + 7^5$	$20132 := -2^6 + 0^1 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 2^9$
$19425 := -1^1 - 9^2 + 4^7 - 2^1 + 5^5$	$19693 := -1^1 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 3^9$	$20203 := 2^3 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 0^1 + 3^9$
$19434 := -1^1 + 9^1 - 4^0 + 3^9 - 4^4$	$19723 := -1^1 - 9^1 + 7^2 + 2^0 + 3^9$	$20213 := 2^4 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 1^0 + 3^9$
$19436 := -1^1 + 9^1 - 4^4 + 3^9 + 6^0$	$19730 := -1^1 - 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 0^1$	$20223 := -2^2 + 0^1 + 2^5 + 2^9 + 3^9$
$19443 := -1^1 + 9^0 - 4^4 + 4^2 + 3^9$	$19731 := -1^1 + 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 - 1^0$	$20232 := 2^2 + 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 2^9$
$19445 := -1^1 + 9^0 - 4^3 + 4^7 + 5^5$	$19732 := 1^1 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 3^9 + 2^5$	$20235 := -2^3 - 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^4$
$19463 := -1^1 + 9^0 - 4^4 + 6^2 + 3^9$	$19732 := -1^1 - 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 2^1$	$20236 := 2^2 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 6^2$
$19532 := -1^1 - 9^1 - 5^3 + 3^9 - 2^4$	$19733 := -1^1 + 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 3^9$	$20237 := -2^3 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 7^2$
$19534 := -1^1 - 9^0 + 5^5 + 3^3 + 4^7$	$19733 := 1^1 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 3^7$	$20243 := -2^4 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 4^3 + 3^9$
$19537 := -1^1 - 9^2 + 5^4 + 3^7 + 7^5$	$19734 := -1^1 - 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 4^1$	$20243 := 2^5 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 3^9$
$19538 := -1^1 - 9^2 + 5^0 + 3^9 - 8^2$	$19735 := 1^1 + 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 5^0$	$20253 := 2^5 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 3^9$
$19539 := -1^1 - 9^1 - 5^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$19735 := -1^1 - 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 5^1$	$20253 := -2^6 + 0^0 + 2^3 + 5^4 + 3^9$
$19553 := -1^1 - 9^1 + 5^1 - 5^3 + 3^9$	$19736 := 1^1 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 3^9 + 6^2$	$20263 := 2^5 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 3^9$
$19559 := -1^1 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 5^6 + 9^3$	$19736 := -1^1 - 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 6^1$	$20273 := -2^3 - 0^0 + 2^8 + 7^3 + 3^9$
$19573 := -1^1 + 9^1 - 5^3 + 7^1 + 3^9$	$19737 := -1^1 - 9^0 + 7^1 + 3^9 + 7^2$	$20293 := 2^4 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 9^2 + 3^9$
$19586 := -1^1 - 9^5 + 5^7 + 8^3 - 6^0$	$19738 := -1^1 - 9^0 - 7^1 + 3^9 + 8^2$	$20293 := -2^7 + 0^0 + 2^3 + 9^3 + 3^9$
$19588 := -1^1 - 9^5 + 5^7 + 8^0 + 8^3$	$19739 := -1^1 - 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$20305 := -2^1 - 0^0 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 5^4$
$19593 := -1^1 - 9^1 + 5^0 - 9^2 + 3^9$	$19743 := 1^1 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 4^0 + 3^9$	$20322 := -2^1 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^7 + 2^9$
$19603 := -1^1 - 9^2 + 6^0 + 0^0 + 3^9$	$19752 := -1^1 + 9^4 - 7^4 + 5^6 - 2^5$	$20324 := 2^6 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 4^3$
$19623 := -1^1 - 9^0 + 6^1 - 2^6 + 3^9$	$19763 := -1^1 + 9^2 - 7^0 + 6^0 + 3^9$	$20324 := -2^7 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 4^4$
$19624 := -1^1 + 9^3 - 6^6 + 2^4 + 4^8$	$19773 := 1^1 + 9^2 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 3^9$	$20325 := 2^2 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 5^3$
$19632 := -1^1 - 9^2 - 6^0 + 3^9 + 2^5$	$19785 := -1^1 + 9^4 - 7^4 + 8^0 + 5^6$	$20325 := -2^4 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^5 + 5^4$
$19636 := -1^1 - 9^1 - 6^0 + 3^9 - 6^2$	$19830 := 1^1 + 9^2 + 8^2 + 3^9 + 0^0$	$20328 := 2^2 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^7 + 8^3$
$19638 := -1^1 - 9^1 - 6^2 + 3^9 + 8^0$	$19843 := -1^1 + 9^2 + 8^2 + 4^2 + 3^9$	$20332 := -2^4 + 0^1 + 3^6 + 3^9 - 2^6$

$20343 := -2^2 - 0^0 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 3^9$	$20414 := -2^6 - 0^0 + 4^6 - 1^0 + 4^7$	$20484 := -2^2 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 8^1 + 4^7$
$20344 := -2^7 + 0^0 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 4^7$	$20418 := -2^6 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 8^4$	$20485 := 2^2 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 5^0$
$20345 := 2^5 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^4$	$20424 := -2^6 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 2^3 + 4^7$	$20486 := 2^2 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 6^0$
$20347 := -2^4 - 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 7^3$	$20433 := 2^2 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 3^6 + 3^9$	$20489 := 2^3 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 9^0$
$20347 := 2^6 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 7^3$	$20433 := -2^5 + 0^0 + 4^5 + 3^9 - 3^5$	$20493 := 2^4 + 0^0 + 4^3 + 9^3 + 3^9$
$20348 := -2^7 - 0^0 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 8^4$	$20434 := -2^4 - 0^0 - 4^4 + 3^9 + 4^5$	$20494 := 2^2 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 9^1 + 4^7$
$20349 := -2^6 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 9^3$	$20435 := -2^3 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 3^9 - 5^6$	$20495 := 2^8 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 9^3 + 5^5$
$20352 := 2^5 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 2^9$	$20438 := -2^5 - 0^0 + 4^7 - 3^2 + 8^4$	$20498 := 2^3 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 9^1 + 8^4$
$20353 := -2^6 + 0^1 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 3^9$	$20443 := -2^3 + 0^1 - 4^4 + 4^5 + 3^9$	$20498 := -2^6 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 8^4$
$20356 := 2^9 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 6^2$	$20444 := -2^5 + 0^1 - 4^1 + 4^6 + 4^7$	$20532 := -2^5 + 0^1 + 5^4 + 3^9 + 2^8$
$20372 := 2^7 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 2^9$	$20446 := -2^5 - 0^0 + 4^6 + 4^7 - 6^0$	$20533 := -2^2 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 3^6 + 3^9$
$20373 := -2^5 + 0^1 + 3^6 - 7^1 + 3^9$	$20447 := -2^5 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 4^7 - 7^0$	$20536 := 2^9 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 6^3$
$20375 := -2^5 + 0^1 + 3^9 - 7^4 + 5^5$	$20448 := -2^4 + 0^1 - 4^2 + 4^7 + 8^4$	$20539 := 2^1 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 9^3$
$20377 := 2^3 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 7^3 + 7^3$	$20449 := -2^5 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 9^0$	$20572 := 2^7 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 2^9$
$20379 := -2^5 + 0^1 + 3^9 - 7^0 + 9^3$	$20453 := 2^1 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 5^6 + 3^6$	$20597 := -2^6 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 9^3 + 7^5$
$20384 := -2^4 + 0^0 - 3^4 + 8^4 + 4^7$	$20453 := -2^7 - 0^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 3^9$	$20633 := 2^2 + 0^0 + 6^3 + 3^6 + 3^9$
$20385 := 2^6 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 8^3 + 5^3$	$20454 := -2^5 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 4^7$	$20635 := -2^8 + 0^0 - 6^4 + 3^8 + 5^6$
$20385 := -2^6 - 0^0 + 3^6 + 8^4 + 5^6$	$20458 := -2^4 - 0^0 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 8^4$	$20636 := -2^7 + 0^0 - 6^3 + 3^9 + 6^4$
$20387 := -2^9 - 0^0 - 3^1 + 8^4 + 7^5$	$20459 := 2^3 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 5^6 + 9^3$	$20643 := -2^6 + 0^0 - 6^0 + 4^5 + 3^9$
$20388 := 2^7 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 8^3$	$20463 := -2^9 + 0^1 - 4^1 + 6^4 + 3^9$	$20644 := 2^7 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 4^6 + 4^7$
$20389 := -2^5 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 8^1 + 9^3$	$20464 := -2^4 - 0^0 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 4^7$	$20647 := -2^8 + 0^0 - 6^0 + 4^6 + 7^5$
$20392 := -2^2 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 9^3 - 2^4$	$20473 := -2^9 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 3^4$	$20653 := 2^7 + 0^0 + 6^3 + 5^4 + 3^9$
$20393 := -2^4 + 0^1 - 3^1 + 9^3 + 3^9$	$20474 := -2^2 - 0^0 + 4^6 - 7^0 + 4^7$	$20673 := -2^8 - 0^0 + 6^4 - 7^2 + 3^9$
$20394 := -2^1 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 9^3 - 4^2$	$20478 := -2^1 - 0^0 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 8^4$	$20678 := -2^3 - 0^0 - 6^3 + 7^5 + 8^4$
$20395 := -2^4 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 9^3 - 5^0$	$20479 := -2^6 - 0^0 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^4$	$20693 := 2^6 + 0^0 + 6^3 + 9^3 + 3^9$
$20396 := -2^4 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 9^3 - 6^0$	$20480 := -2^1 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 0^0$	$20739 := -2^4 + 0^1 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 9^3$
$20397 := -2^3 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 9^3 - 7^1$	$20482 := -2^1 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 2^2$	$20742 := -2^5 - 0^0 + 7^5 + 4^6 - 2^7$
$20398 := -2^4 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 9^3 + 8^0$	$20483 := 2^1 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 3^0$	$20744 := 2^8 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 4^6 + 4^7$
$20399 := -2^2 + 0^1 + 3^9 - 9^1 + 9^3$	$20484 := 2^1 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 8^4 + 4^7$	$20745 := -2^5 - 0^0 + 7^5 + 4^6 - 5^3$
		$20768 := -2^7 - 0^0 + 7^5 - 6^1 + 8^4$
		$20774 := -2^7 + 0^1 - 7^0 + 7^5 + 4^6$
		$20782 := -2^7 - 0^0 + 7^5 + 8^4 + 2^3$

$20783 := -2^7 - 0^0 + 7^5 + 8^4 + 3^2$	$21236 := -2^8 + 1^0 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 6^4$	$22235 := 2^4 + 2^0 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^6$
$20784 := -2^7 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^6$	$21345 := 2^9 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^3$	$22235 := -2^4 + 2^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^6$
$20789 := -2^5 - 0^0 + 7^5 + 8^4 - 9^2$	$21347 := -2^5 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 7^4$	$22243 := 2^9 + 2^9 + 2^9 + 4^5 + 3^9$
$20837 := -2^6 - 0^0 + 8^4 - 3^0 + 7^5$	$21348 := 2^7 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^3$	$22243 := -2^9 - 2^9 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 3^9$
$20843 := 2^7 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 3^9$	$21362 := -2^7 - 1^0 + 3^9 + 6^4 + 2^9$	$22253 := 2^1 + 2^0 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 3^8$
$20847 := -2^6 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 4^6 + 7^5$	$21363 := -2^9 - 1^0 + 3^7 + 6^1 + 3^9$	$22259 := 2^3 + 2^0 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 9^4$
$20853 := 2^5 + 0^0 + 8^3 + 5^4 + 3^9$	$21364 := 2^7 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 6^4 + 4^4$	$22304 := -2^7 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 0^0 + 4^7$
$20864 := -2^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 6^5 - 4^6$	$21417 := 2^9 + 1^0 + 4^6 + 1^0 + 7^5$	$22305 := -2^9 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 5^5$
$20870 := -2^5 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 + 0^1$	$21433 := -2^1 - 1^0 + 4^5 + 3^6 + 3^9$	$22315 := 2^6 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 5^6$
$20871 := -2^5 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 - 1^0$	$21436 := 2^9 + 1^0 + 4^5 + 3^9 + 6^3$	$22315 := -2^7 + 2^8 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 5^6$
$20872 := -2^4 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 - 2^4$	$21439 := 2^1 + 1^0 + 4^5 + 3^9 + 9^3$	$22334 := -2^5 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 3^9 - 4^2$
$20873 := -2^1 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 - 3^3$	$21497 := 2^9 + 1^0 + 4^6 + 9^2 + 7^5$	$22335 := 2^2 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 3^8 + 5^6$
$20874 := -2^5 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 + 4^1$	$21634 := -2^4 + 1^0 - 6^4 + 3^8 + 4^7$	$22335 := -2^5 - 2^7 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 5^4$
$20875 := -2^1 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 - 5^2$	$21693 := -2^4 + 1^0 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 3^9$	$22337 := 2^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 3^9 + 7^4$
$20876 := -2^5 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 + 6^1$	$21785 := 2^8 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 8^4 + 5^4$	$22337 := -2^1 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 3^9 + 7^4$
$20877 := -2^5 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^1 + 7^5$	$21837 := -2^8 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 3^9 + 7^4$	$22339 := -2^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 9^3$
$20878 := -2^4 - 0^0 - 8^1 + 7^5 + 8^4$	$21893 := -2^8 + 1^0 - 8^4 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$22347 := -2^8 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3$
$20879 := -2^4 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 - 9^1$	$21925 := -2^2 - 1^0 + 9^4 - 2^8 + 5^6$	$22352 := -2^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^5 - 2^9$
$20887 := -2^3 + 0^1 - 8^1 + 8^4 + 7^5$	$21945 := -2^8 - 1^0 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 5^6$	$22353 := -2^3 + 2^8 - 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^8$
$20893 := -2^5 + 0^0 + 8^3 + 9^3 + 3^9$	$21965 := -2^2 - 1^0 + 9^4 - 6^3 + 5^6$	$22355 := 2^4 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 5^6$
$20897 := -2^2 - 0^0 + 8^4 - 9^0 + 7^5$	$21984 := -2^7 + 1^0 - 9^4 + 8^5 - 4^6$	$22355 := -2^9 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^5 - 5^1$
$20923 := -2^1 + 0^0 + 9^3 + 2^9 + 3^9$	$22037 := -2^4 - 2^5 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 7^4$	$22357 := -2^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 7^4$
$20932 := 2^3 + 0^1 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 2^9$	$22053 := -2^2 - 2^7 - 0^0 + 5^6 + 3^8$	$22357 := 2^4 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 5^0 + 7^4$
$20933 := 2^9 + 0^1 + 9^1 + 3^6 + 3^9$	$22059 := -2^6 - 2^6 + 0^0 + 5^6 + 9^4$	$22358 := -2^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^5 - 8^3$
$20963 := -2^3 + 0^0 - 9^1 + 6^4 + 3^9$	$22073 := -2^1 - 2^3 - 0^0 + 7^4 + 3^9$	$22359 := -2^1 + 2^8 - 3^4 + 5^6 + 9^4$
$20963 := 2^6 + 0^0 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 3^8$	$22153 := -2^1 - 2^5 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 3^8$	$22364 := -2^9 - 2^0 - 3^9 + 6^6 - 4^6$
$20973 := 2^9 + 0^1 + 9^3 + 7^2 + 3^9$	$22159 := -2^5 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 9^4$	$22372 := 2^4 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 2^8$
$20987 := 2^1 + 0^0 + 9^2 + 8^4 + 7^5$	$22195 := 2^2 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 5^6$	$22372 := -2^5 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 2^8$
$21236 := 2^7 + 1^0 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 6^4$	$22195 := -2^3 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 5^6$	$22373 := -2^4 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^1 + 3^9$
		$22373 := 2^5 + 2^7 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 3^9$
		$22374 := -2^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 7^5 - 4^5$
		$22374 := 2^1 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 4^4$

$22375 := 2^7 + 2^7 + 3^7 + 7^5 + 5^5$	$22473 := -2^7 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 3^8$	$22635 := -2^6 + 2^9 + 6^0 + 3^8 + 5^6$
$22375 := -2^7 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 7^2 + 5^5$	$22483 := -2^4 - 2^8 - 4^5 + 8^4 + 3^9$	$22643 := 2^7 + 2^9 + 6^4 + 4^5 + 3^9$
$22376 := -2^2 - 2^4 - 3^7 + 7^5 + 6^5$	$22489 := -2^3 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 8^2 + 9^4$	$22647 := -2^6 + 2^9 + 6^4 + 4^6 + 7^5$
$22376 := 2^7 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 6^2$	$22496 := -2^9 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 9^4 - 6^0$	$22649 := -2^2 - 2^8 - 6^2 + 4^7 + 9^4$
$22378 := -2^4 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^5 + 8^5$	$22498 := -2^9 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 8^2$	$22659 := 2^8 + 2^0 + 6^3 + 5^6 + 9^4$
$22379 := -2^2 - 2^8 - 3^6 + 7^5 + 9^4$	$22532 := -2^2 - 2^4 + 5^5 + 3^9 - 2^8$	$22665 := -2^3 - 2^9 - 6^3 + 6^5 + 5^6$
$22383 := 2^8 + 2^8 + 3^7 + 8^0 + 3^9$	$22533 := -2^4 - 2^4 + 5^5 - 3^5 + 3^9$	$22687 := -2^5 + 2^7 - 6^5 + 8^5 - 7^4$
$22393 := 2^1 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 9^1 + 3^9$	$22533 := 2^6 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 3^3 + 3^8$	$22694 := -2^8 - 2^0 + 6^1 + 9^4 + 4^7$
$22395 := -2^1 - 2^5 + 3^5 + 9^4 + 5^6$	$22534 := -2^1 - 2^4 + 5^5 + 3^9 - 4^4$	$22695 := -2^1 + 2^9 - 6^0 + 9^4 + 5^6$
$22395 := 2^6 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 9^4 + 5^6$	$22535 := -2^4 - 2^8 - 5^0 + 3^9 + 5^5$	$22729 := -2^7 - 2^9 + 7^5 + 2^0 + 9^4$
$22423 := -2^1 - 2^3 + 4^7 - 2^9 + 3^8$	$22536 := -2^3 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 3^6 + 6^5$	$22732 := 2^3 + 2^7 + 7^4 + 3^9 + 2^9$
$22429 := -2^1 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 2^9 + 9^4$	$22537 := 2^2 + 2^2 + 5^6 + 3^8 + 7^3$	$22732 := -2^7 + 2^2 + 7^5 + 3^8 - 2^9$
$22430 := -2^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 3^8 - 0^0$	$22537 := -2^3 + 2^4 + 5^6 + 3^8 + 7^3$	$22733 := 2^3 + 2^9 + 7^3 + 3^7 + 3^9$
$22431 := -2^9 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 3^8 - 1^0$	$22538 := 2^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$22733 := -2^4 - 2^6 + 7^4 + 3^6 + 3^9$
$22432 := -2^1 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 3^8 - 2^9$	$22538 := -2^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 3^8 + 8^3$	$22734 := -2^2 - 2^8 + 7^2 + 3^8 + 4^7$
$22433 := -2^9 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 3^0 + 3^8$	$22539 := -2^2 - 2^8 + 5^5 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$22735 := -2^1 - 2^6 - 7^1 + 3^9 + 5^5$
$22434 := -2^8 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 3^8 + 4^7$	$22539 := 2^4 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 3^4 + 9^4$	$22737 := -2^5 - 2^8 - 7^3 + 3^8 + 7^5$
$22435 := -2^3 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 3^8 + 5^6$	$22543 := -2^3 - 2^0 + 5^5 - 4^4 + 3^9$	$22753 := -2^1 - 2^2 - 7^2 + 5^5 + 3^9$
$22436 := -2^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 3^8 + 6^0$	$22553 := -2^1 - 2^7 - 5^3 + 5^5 + 3^9$	$22753 := 2^5 + 2^9 + 7^4 + 5^3 + 3^9$
$22438 := -2^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 3^8 + 8^0$	$22554 := -2^4 - 2^6 + 5^5 + 5^5 + 4^7$	$22773 := 2^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 7^4 + 3^9$
$22443 := -2^8 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 3^7$	$22558 := -2^5 - 2^8 + 5^5 + 5^6 + 8^4$	$22773 := -2^8 + 2^2 - 7^3 + 7^5 + 3^8$
$22447 := 2^3 + 2^9 + 4^5 + 4^6 + 7^5$	$22559 := -2^3 + 2^8 + 5^3 + 5^6 + 9^4$	$22791 := -2^6 - 2^9 + 7^5 + 9^4 - 1^0$
$22449 := -2^8 + 2^4 - 4^4 + 4^7 + 9^4$	$22573 := -2^3 - 2^7 + 5^4 + 7^4 + 3^9$	$22792 := -2^5 - 2^5 + 7^5 + 9^4 - 2^9$
$22459 := 2^4 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 9^4$	$22593 := -2^8 + 2^5 + 5^5 + 9^1 + 3^9$	$22793 := -2^2 - 2^4 + 7^4 + 9^3 + 3^9$
$22459 := -2^9 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 9^4$	$22595 := 2^7 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 9^4 + 5^6$	$22794 := -2^4 - 2^7 - 7^1 + 9^4 + 4^7$
$22463 := -2^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 3^9$	$22595 := -2^7 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 9^4 + 5^6$	$22795 := -2^9 + 2^6 + 7^5 + 9^4 - 5^3$
$22464 := -2^8 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^6 + 4^8$	$22597 := 2^2 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 9^4 + 7^3$	$22834 := -2^7 + 2^4 + 8^0 + 3^8 + 4^7$
$22466 := -2^5 + 2^1 - 4^7 + 6^6 - 6^5$	$22624 := -2^9 - 2^9 + 6^5 - 2^9 + 4^7$	$22835 := -2^2 + 2^5 - 8^0 + 3^9 + 5^5$
$22469 := -2^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 9^4$	$22625 := -2^3 - 2^8 + 6^5 - 2^9 + 5^6$	$22846 := -2^1 - 2^7 + 8^4 + 4^8 - 6^6$
		$22847 := -2^1 - 2^5 + 8^4 + 4^7 + 7^4$
		$22849 := -2^4 - 2^4 - 8^2 + 4^7 + 9^4$
		$22855 := 2^3 + 2^0 + 8^4 + 5^5 + 5^6$

$$\begin{aligned} 22856 &:= -2^5 - 2^0 - 8^3 + 5^6 + 6^5 & 22954 &:= -2^2 + 2^3 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 4^7 & 23087 &:= -2^1 + 3^7 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 7^5 \\ 22863 &:= -2^4 + 2^1 - 8^4 + 6^6 - 3^9 & 22955 &:= 2^4 + 2^7 + 9^4 + 5^4 + 5^6 & 23127 &:= -2^8 + 3^8 - 1^0 + 2^4 + 7^5 \\ 22865 &:= -2^3 - 2^4 - 8^3 + 6^5 + 5^6 & 22958 &:= 2^2 + 2^8 + 9^4 + 5^6 + 8^3 & 23145 &:= -2^3 + 3^9 - 1^0 + 4^6 - 5^4 \\ 22873 &:= -2^9 + 2^4 + 8^0 + 7^5 + 3^8 & 22964 &:= 2^1 + 2^4 + 9^4 + 6^0 + 4^7 & 23146 &:= -2^4 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 4^7 + 6^3 \\ 22874 &:= -2^3 + 2^0 + 8^4 + 7^4 + 4^7 & 22964 &:= -2^4 - 2^0 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 4^7 & 23163 &:= -2^1 + 3^7 - 1^0 + 6^4 + 3^9 \\ 22883 &:= -2^7 - 2^8 - 8^3 + 8^4 + 3^9 & 22973 &:= 2^5 + 2^7 + 9^3 + 7^4 + 3^9 & 23164 &:= 2^1 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 6^3 + 4^7 \\ 22904 &:= -2^3 - 2^5 + 9^4 - 0^0 + 4^7 & 22974 &:= -2^2 - 2^4 + 9^4 + 7^2 + 4^7 & 23204 &:= 2^1 + 3^8 + 2^8 + 0^0 + 4^7 \\ 22914 &:= -2^4 - 2^4 + 9^4 + 1^0 + 4^7 & 22975 &:= -2^6 - 2^7 + 9^6 - 7^6 - 5^8 & 23204 &:= -2^6 + 3^9 - 2^9 + 0^0 + 4^6 \\ 22924 &:= -2^2 - 2^0 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 4^7 & 22977 &:= -2^4 - 2^5 + 9^4 - 7^3 + 7^5 & 23234 &:= -2^2 + 3^9 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^7 \\ 22934 &:= -2^1 - 2^3 - 9^0 + 3^8 + 4^7 & 22994 &:= 2^3 + 2^5 + 9^1 + 9^4 + 4^7 & 23234 &:= 2^5 + 3^0 + 2^8 + 3^8 + 4^7 \\ 22935 &:= -2^1 + 2^7 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 5^5 & 22994 &:= -2^4 - 2^4 + 9^2 + 9^4 + 4^7 & 23235 &:= -2^2 - 3^4 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 5^5 \\ 22935 &:= 2^2 + 2^4 + 9^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 & 22995 &:= 2^4 + 2^6 + 9^3 + 9^4 + 5^6 & 23235 &:= 2^6 + 3^6 + 2^8 + 3^8 + 5^6 \\ 22937 &:= -2^2 + 2^7 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 7^4 & 23034 &:= 2^3 + 3^4 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 4^7 & 23237 &:= -2^1 - 3^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^5 \\ 22938 &:= -2^7 + 2^4 - 9^3 + 3^9 + 8^4 & 23034 &:= -2^4 - 3^6 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 & 23237 &:= 2^9 + 3^7 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 7^3 \\ 22940 &:= -2^1 - 2^1 + 9^4 + 4^7 - 0^0 & 23035 &:= -2^4 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 5^5 & 23238 &:= -2^1 - 3^3 - 2^9 + 3^9 + 8^4 \\ 22941 &:= -2^1 - 2^0 + 9^4 + 4^7 - 1^0 & 23042 &:= 2^5 + 3^8 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 2^6 & 23239 &:= 2^7 + 3^7 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 9^3 \\ 22942 &:= -2^1 + 2^0 + 9^4 + 4^7 - 2^1 & 23042 &:= -2^5 + 3^8 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 2^7 & 23252 &:= -2^2 + 3^9 - 2^6 + 5^5 + 2^9 \\ 22943 &:= -2^1 + 2^0 - 9^0 + 4^7 + 3^8 & 23043 &:= -2^3 - 3^6 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 3^9 & 23253 &:= -2^6 - 3^1 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 3^9 \\ 22944 &:= -2^1 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 4^7 - 4^0 & 23043 &:= 2^4 + 3^4 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 3^8 & 23254 &:= -2^1 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 5^5 - 4^3 \\ 22945 &:= -2^1 + 2^0 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 5^0 & 23046 &:= 2^6 + 3^8 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 6^2 & 23255 &:= -2^6 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 5^5 - 5^0 \\ 22946 &:= -2^1 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 6^0 & 23049 &:= -2^1 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 4^6 - 9^3 & 23256 &:= -2^3 - 3^2 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 \\ 22947 &:= -2^2 - 2^0 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 23053 &:= 2^1 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 3^9 & 23257 &:= -2^3 + 3^8 - 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\ 22948 &:= -2^1 + 2^2 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 8^0 & 23054 &:= -2^4 + 3^8 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 4^7 & 23258 &:= -2^6 + 3^9 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\ 22949 &:= 2^1 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 4^7 + 9^4 & 23056 &:= 2^5 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 6^3 & 23264 &:= -2^2 + 3^9 - 2^9 + 6^0 + 4^6 \\ 22949 &:= -2^2 - 2^0 + 9^1 + 4^7 + 9^4 & 23065 &:= 2^8 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 5^5 & 23265 &:= -2^7 - 3^2 + 2^0 + 6^5 + 5^6 \\ 22952 &:= -2^1 + 2^8 + 9^4 + 5^6 + 2^9 & 23065 &:= -2^8 - 3^4 + 0^0 + 6^5 + 5^6 & 23268 &:= -2^8 + 3^9 - 2^8 + 6^0 + 8^4 \\ 22953 &:= 2^3 + 2^7 + 9^1 + 5^5 + 3^9 & 23074 &:= -2^4 + 3^7 + 0^1 + 7^5 + 4^6 & 23271 &:= -2^5 + 3^8 - 2^6 + 7^5 - 1^0 \\ 22953 &:= -2^6 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 3^9 & 23074 &:= 2^7 + 3^8 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 4^7 & 23272 &:= -2^4 + 3^8 - 2^4 + 7^5 - 2^6 \\ 22954 &:= 2^1 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 4^7 & 23076 &:= -2^8 + 3^8 + 0^1 + 7^5 - 6^2 & 23273 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 - 2^6 + 7^5 + 3^8 \\ & & & & 23274 &:= -2^4 + 3^8 + 2^1 + 7^3 + 4^7 \\ & & & & 23275 &:= -2^2 + 3^8 - 2^6 + 7^5 - 5^2 \\ & & & & 23276 &:= -2^2 - 3^8 - 2^3 - 7^5 + 6^6 \end{aligned}$$

$23277 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 2^8 + 7^5 - 7^3$	$23370 := -2^1 + 3^1 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 0^0$	$23436 := 2^5 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^8 + 6^3$
$23278 := -2^4 - 3^8 - 2^9 - 7^4 + 8^5$	$23372 := 2^1 + 3^0 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 2^0$	$23437 := 2^1 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 3^8 + 7^5$
$23279 := -2^2 - 3^4 - 2^2 + 7^5 + 9^4$	$23372 := -2^2 + 3^2 + 3^8 + 7^5 - 2^0$	$23437 := -2^1 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 3^9 - 7^3$
$23282 := -2^9 + 3^9 - 2^0 + 8^4 + 2^4$	$23374 := 2^1 + 3^1 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 4^0$	$23438 := -2^2 - 3^4 - 4^4 + 3^9 + 8^4$
$23284 := -2^9 + 3^9 + 2^0 + 8^4 + 4^2$	$23374 := -2^1 + 3^2 + 3^8 + 7^5 - 4^0$	$23438 := 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 3^9 + 8^3$
$23297 := -2^2 - 3^1 - 2^6 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$23376 := -2^1 + 3^2 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 6^0$	$23439 := 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^5 + 9^4$
$23307 := -2^6 + 3^1 + 3^8 + 0^1 + 7^5$	$23376 := 2^2 + 3^1 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 6^0$	$23439 := -2^4 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 3^9 - 9^2$
$23324 := 2^3 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 2^7 + 4^7$	$23378 := 2^3 + 3^0 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 8^0$	$23442 := -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 4^7 + 2^9$
$23325 := 2^1 + 3^1 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 5^5$	$23378 := -2^4 + 3^3 + 3^8 + 7^5 - 8^0$	$23443 := -2^8 - 3^4 + 4^0 + 4^6 + 3^9$
$23325 := -2^2 + 3^2 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 5^5$	$23382 := -2^7 + 3^5 + 3^9 + 8^4 - 2^9$	$23448 := -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 4^7 + 8^3$
$23326 := 2^5 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 2^7 + 6^4$	$23384 := -2^6 - 3^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 4^7$	$23452 := 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 2^9$
$23327 := 2^1 + 3^6 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 7^4$	$23385 := -2^4 + 3^4 + 3^9 + 8^3 + 5^5$	$23454 := 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 4^7$
$23327 := -2^3 - 3^0 + 3^8 - 2^5 + 7^5$	$23385 := 2^6 + 3^0 + 3^9 + 8^3 + 5^5$	$23456 := -2^3 - 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^5$
$23328 := -2^9 - 3^1 + 3^9 + 2^6 + 8^4$	$23387 := 2^1 + 3^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 7^5$	$23457 := -2^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 5^2 - 7^3$
$23342 := -2^6 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 2^9$	$23387 := -2^4 + 3^3 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 7^5$	$23458 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 8^3$
$23343 := 2^7 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^8$	$23406 := -2^9 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 0^0 + 6^5$	$23459 := 2^9 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 9^4$
$23344 := -2^7 - 3^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 4^6$	$23416 := -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 6^5$	$23462 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 2^9$
$23345 := 2^5 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^3$	$23417 := -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 1^0 + 7^5$	$23464 := 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 4^7$
$23345 := -2^8 + 3^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^5$	$23417 := 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 1^0 + 7^5$	$23465 := -2^4 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 6^5 + 5^6$
$23346 := -2^2 - 3^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^5$	$23419 := -2^8 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 9^4$	$23472 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^5 + 2^5$
$23347 := -2^1 - 3^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^5$	$23424 := -2^5 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 2^9 + 4^7$	$23472 := -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^5 + 2^7$
$23347 := 2^5 + 3^3 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$23426 := -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 2^0 + 6^5$	$23473 := 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 7^5 + 3^8$
$23349 := -2^9 + 3^0 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 9^2$	$23427 := -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 2^6 + 7^5$	$23473 := -2^6 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 7^0 + 3^9$
$23364 := -2^1 + 3^1 + 3^9 + 6^5 - 4^6$	$23432 := -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 3^8 + 2^9$	$23474 := 2^7 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 4^6$
$23365 := -2^3 - 3^0 - 3^3 + 6^5 + 5^6$	$23433 := 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^5 + 3^8$	$23475 := -2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^5 + 5^3$
$23365 := 2^9 + 3^2 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 5^5$	$23433 := -2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 3^4 + 3^9$	$23476 := -2^1 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 7^5 + 6^5$
$23366 := -2^4 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 6^4$	$23434 := -2^3 - 3^4 - 4^4 + 3^9 + 4^6$	$23476 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^5 + 6^2$
$23367 := -2^1 + 3^4 - 3^8 + 6^6 - 7^5$	$23435 := 2^7 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 3^9 + 5^5$	$23477 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 7^5$
$23368 := -2^2 + 3^2 + 3^9 + 6^5 - 8^4$	$23436 := -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 6^5$	$23479 := -2^6 - 3^4 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 9^4$

$23493 := 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 3^3$	$23549 := 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 4^1 + 9^3$	$23646 := -2^6 - 3^8 - 6^0 - 4^7 + 6^6$
$23494 := -2^9 - 3^9 + 4^5 + 9^5 - 4^7$	$23562 := 2^4 + 3^4 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 2^6$	$23648 := -2^6 - 3^8 + 6^6 - 4^7 + 8^0$
$23496 := -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 6^5$	$23563 := 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 3^9$	$23649 := -2^7 + 3^9 - 6^0 + 4^6 - 9^0$
$23496 := 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 6^2$	$23564 := -2^4 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 4^3$	$23652 := -2^1 - 3^1 + 6^5 + 5^6 + 2^8$
$23497 := -2^4 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$23566 := 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 6^5$	$23652 := 2^2 + 3^5 + 6^5 + 5^6 + 2^2$
$23497 := 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$23567 := -2^4 + 3^8 - 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5$	$23653 := 2^3 + 3^0 + 6^5 + 5^6 + 3^5$
$23498 := 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 8^3$	$23568 := 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^3$	$23654 := -2^1 - 3^0 + 6^5 + 5^6 + 4^4$
$23499 := -2^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 9^3 + 9^4$	$23569 := -2^2 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^3$	$23655 := 2^7 + 3^0 + 6^5 + 5^3 + 5^6$
$23523 := -2^4 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 2^1 + 3^9$	$23582 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^4 - 2^6$	$23655 := -2^7 - 3^5 + 6^5 + 5^4 + 5^6$
$23524 := -2^8 + 3^9 - 5^0 + 2^1 + 4^6$	$23583 := -2^9 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 8^4 + 3^7$	$23656 := -2^6 + 3^3 - 6^5 + 5^7 - 6^6$
$23526 := -2^1 - 3^0 + 5^6 + 2^7 + 6^5$	$23584 := 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^3 + 4^7$	$23657 := 2^7 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$
$23527 := 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 2^5 + 7^5$	$23584 := -2^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^4 - 4^4$	$23657 := -2^8 - 3^8 + 6^6 + 5^4 - 7^5$
$23528 := -2^7 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 2^1 + 8^4$	$23585 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^4 - 5^3$	$23658 := -2^7 + 3^9 + 6^1 + 5^0 + 8^4$
$23529 := -2^4 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 2^3 + 9^3$	$23586 := -2^1 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^4 - 6^3$	$23659 := 2^8 + 3^0 + 6^5 + 5^6 + 9^0$
$23529 := 2^7 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 2^9 + 9^2$	$23587 := -2^7 + 3^7 + 5^4 + 8^4 + 7^5$	$23672 := -2^7 - 3^8 + 6^6 - 7^5 + 2^9$
$23530 := -2^3 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 3^9 + 0^0$	$23588 := -2^1 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^4 - 8^2$	$23673 := 2^3 + 3^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 3^8$
$23532 := -2^2 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 3^9 - 2^0$	$23589 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^4 - 9^0$	$23674 := -2^5 + 3^9 + 6^5 + 7^3 - 4^6$
$23534 := -2^1 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 3^9 - 4^0$	$23617 := 2^5 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 1^0 + 7^5$	$23674 := 2^9 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 7^0 + 4^7$
$23536 := -2^1 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 3^9 + 6^0$	$23627 := 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^0 + 2^8 + 7^5$	$23675 := -2^8 - 3^3 + 6^5 + 7^5 - 5^4$
$23542 := -2^5 + 3^8 + 5^4 + 4^7 + 2^2$	$23634 := -2^2 + 3^6 - 6^2 + 3^8 + 4^7$	$23676 := -2^4 - 3^7 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 6^5$
$23543 := 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 4^1 + 3^9$	$23635 := -2^3 - 3^0 + 6^5 + 3^5 + 5^6$	$23677 := -2^7 - 3^6 + 6^5 - 7^2 + 7^5$
$23543 := -2^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 3^8$	$23636 := -2^4 + 3^8 - 6^4 + 3^9 - 6^4$	$23678 := -2^5 - 3^3 + 6^5 - 7^5 + 8^5$
$23544 := -2^2 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 4^6 - 4^4$	$23637 := 2^7 + 3^7 + 6^4 + 3^9 + 7^3$	$23679 := 2^5 + 3^5 + 6^2 + 7^5 + 9^4$
$23546 := -2^4 + 3^3 - 5^4 + 4^7 + 6^5$	$23639 := -2^8 + 3^7 + 6^4 + 3^9 + 9^3$	$23679 := -2^8 + 3^4 + 6^5 + 7^5 - 9^3$
$23546 := 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 4^2 + 6^5$	$23640 := -2^9 - 3^2 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 0^0$	$23680 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 + 8^4 + 0^0$
$23547 := -2^4 + 3^8 + 5^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$23642 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 6^0 + 4^6 - 2^7$	$23682 := -2^5 + 3^9 - 6^0 + 8^4 - 2^6$
$23548 := 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^4 + 4^7 + 8^4$	$23643 := -2^5 + 3^6 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 3^8$	$23683 := -2^4 - 3^4 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 3^9$
$23548 := -2^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 4^6 + 8^4$	$23644 := -2^7 + 3^9 - 6^1 + 4^6 - 4^0$	$23684 := -2^5 + 3^9 + 6^0 + 8^4 - 4^3$
$23549 := -2^2 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 4^2 + 9^3$	$23645 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 6^0 + 4^6 - 5^3$	$23685 := 2^8 + 3^3 + 6^5 + 8^0 + 5^6$
		$23686 := -2^7 + 3^9 - 6^0 + 8^4 + 6^2$
		$23688 := -2^7 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 8^0 + 8^4$
		$23689 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 6^0 + 8^4 - 9^2$

$23694 := -2^3 - 3^2 + 6^6 - 9^4 - 4^7$	$23764 := 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 6^4 + 4^4$	$23832 := -2^1 - 3^2 + 8^4 + 3^9 + 2^6$
$23697 := 2^5 + 3^4 + 6^3 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$23765 := -2^6 - 3^6 + 7^5 + 6^5 - 5^2$	$23834 := -2^3 - 3^0 + 8^2 + 3^9 + 4^6$
$23707 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 0^1 + 7^5$	$23768 := -2^1 - 3^8 - 7^4 - 6^2 + 8^5$	$23835 := 2^2 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 3^9 + 5^2$
$23708 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 7^1 + 0^1 + 8^4$	$23769 := -2^2 - 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^5 - 9^3$	$23836 := -2^8 + 3^6 - 8^4 + 3^9 + 6^5$
$23723 := -2^4 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 2^7 + 3^8$	$23776 := 2^6 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 7^5 + 6^0$	$23837 := 2^3 + 3^0 + 8^4 + 3^9 + 7^2$
$23724 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 7^2 + 2^1 + 4^6$	$23781 := -2^2 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 8^4 - 1^0$	$23837 := -2^4 - 3^3 + 8^3 + 3^8 + 7^5$
$23726 := -2^6 - 3^6 + 7^5 - 2^6 + 6^5$	$23782 := -2^1 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 8^4 + 2^2$	$23838 := -2^1 - 3^1 + 8^2 + 3^9 + 8^4$
$23727 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 2^3 + 7^5$	$23783 := 2^1 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 8^4 + 3^9$	$23839 := 2^5 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 3^9 + 9^0$
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$23728 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 7^2 + 2^1 + 8^4$	$23784 := -2^1 + 3^9 - 7^0 + 8^1 + 4^6$	$23840 := -2^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 4^6 - 0^0$
$23740 := -2^5 + 3^9 - 7^1 + 4^6 + 0^1$	$23785 := -2^1 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 8^4 + 5^0$	$23842 := -2^1 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 4^6 + 2^6$
$23741 := -2^5 + 3^9 - 7^1 + 4^6 + 1^0$	$23785 := 2^2 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 8^4 + 5^0$	$23843 := -2^4 + 3^4 - 8^0 + 4^6 + 3^9$
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$23743 := -2^1 - 3^3 - 7^1 + 4^6 + 3^9$	$23788 := -2^5 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 8^4 - 8^1$	$23846 := 2^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 4^6 + 6^0$
$23743 := 2^7 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 3^8$	$23789 := 2^1 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 8^4 + 9^0$	$23848 := 2^2 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 4^3 + 8^4$
$23744 := -2^1 + 3^9 - 7^2 + 4^2 + 4^6$	$23789 := -2^3 - 3^2 - 7^4 + 8^5 - 9^4$	$23852 := 2^2 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 5^1 + 2^6$
$23745 := -2^1 + 3^9 - 7^1 + 4^6 - 5^2$	$23803 := -2^2 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 0^0 + 3^9$	$23852 := -2^4 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 5^2 + 2^6$
$23745 := 2^9 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 5^3$	$23804 := 2^3 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 0^0 + 4^2$	$23853 := -2^3 + 3^4 + 8^4 + 5^0 + 3^9$
$23746 := -2^2 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 4^6 - 6^2$	$23812 := 2^4 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 1^0 + 2^4$	$23853 := 2^6 + 3^2 + 8^4 + 5^0 + 3^9$
$23747 := 2^5 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 4^1 + 7^5$	$23812 := -2^5 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 1^0 + 2^6$	$23856 := 2^4 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 5^2 + 6^2$
$23747 := -2^5 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 4^6 - 7^0$	$23813 := 2^5 + 3^0 + 8^4 + 1^0 + 3^9$	$23856 := -2^8 + 3^9 + 8^1 + 5^5 + 6^4$
$23747 := -2^5 + 3^9 - 7^0 + 4^6 + 7^0$	$23817 := -2^6 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 1^0 + 7^5$	$23857 := 2^2 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 5^2 + 7^2$
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$23748 := 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 8^3$	$23823 := 2^4 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 2^0 + 3^9$	$23858 := 2^5 + 3^2 + 8^4 + 5^6 + 8^4$
$23749 := -2^5 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 4^6 + 9^0$	$23826 := -2^4 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 2^6 - 6^0$	$23859 := -2^1 + 3^7 - 8^3 + 5^6 + 9^4$
$23749 := 2^9 + 3^5 + 7^2 + 4^7 + 9^4$	$23827 := -2^1 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 2^0 + 7^2$	$23863 := 2^1 + 3^4 + 8^4 + 6^0 + 3^9$
$23750 := 2^8 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 0^0$	$23828 := 2^4 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 2^5 + 8^4$	$23866 := -2^7 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 6^3 - 6^0$
$23763 := -2^6 - 3^3 + 7^5 + 6^5 - 3^6$	$23828 := -2^4 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 2^6 + 8^4$	$23867 := -2^8 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 6^0 + 7^3$
$23764 := -2^1 + 3^9 - 7^2 + 6^2 + 4^6$	$23829 := -2^5 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 2^0 + 9^2$	$23868 := -2^7 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 6^3 + 8^4$
		$23869 := 2^3 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 6^0 + 9^2$
		$23871 := -2^3 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 7^5 - 1^0$
		$23872 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 7^5 - 2^2$

$23873 := -2^2 - 3^1 + 8^3 + 7^5 + 3^8$	$23964 := -2^5 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 6^3 + 4^6$	$24137 := -2^8 + 4^5 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 7^5$
$23874 := -2^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 7^5 - 4^1$	$23967 := 2^9 + 3^4 + 9^4 + 6^1 + 7^5$	$24137 := 2^9 + 4^4 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 7^5$
$23875 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 7^5 - 5^0$	$23968 := -2^4 - 3^7 - 9^4 - 6^2 + 8^5$	$24146 := -2^4 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 4^7 + 6^5$
$23875 := 2^6 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 7^1 + 5^2$	$23970 := -2^7 + 3^6 + 9^4 + 7^5 + 0^0$	$24156 := -2^2 + 4^7 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 6^5$
$23876 := -2^4 + 3^9 + 8^3 + 7^4 + 6^4$	$23982 := -2^7 - 3^7 + 9^5 - 8^5 + 2^4$	$24157 := 2^7 + 4^6 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 7^5$
$23877 := -2^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 7^5 - 7^0$	$23983 := -2^6 + 3^3 - 9^4 + 8^5 - 3^7$	$24160 := -2^1 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 6^5 + 0^0$
$23879 := -2^1 + 3^0 + 8^3 + 7^5 + 9^4$	$23984 := -2^5 - 3^7 - 9^4 + 8^5 - 4^1$	$24164 := 2^1 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 6^5 + 4^7$
$23891 := -2^7 - 3^7 + 8^5 - 9^4 - 1^0$	$23985 := -2^6 + 3^9 + 9^3 + 8^3 + 5^5$	$24166 := 2^2 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 6^5$
$23892 := -2^4 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 9^0 + 2^7$	$23986 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 9^0 + 8^4 + 6^3$	$24176 := 2^3 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 7^1 + 6^5$
$23892 := 2^4 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 9^2 + 2^4$	$23987 := -2^5 - 3^7 - 9^4 + 8^5 - 7^0$	$24176 := -2^5 + 4^7 - 1^0 + 7^2 + 6^5$
$23893 := 2^5 + 3^0 + 8^4 + 9^2 + 3^9$	$23988 := -2^3 + 3^9 + 9^3 + 8^4 - 8^3$	$24223 := -2^2 + 4^6 - 2^6 + 2^9 + 3^9$
$23893 := -2^7 - 3^7 + 8^5 + 9^0 - 3^8$	$23988 := 2^6 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 8^2 + 8^4$	$24226 := -2^1 + 4^7 + 2^2 + 2^6 + 6^5$
$23897 := 2^3 + 3^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$23989 := -2^5 - 3^7 + 9^0 + 8^5 - 9^4$	$24226 := 2^1 + 4^7 + 2^5 + 2^5 + 6^5$
$23897 := -2^6 + 3^4 + 8^3 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$23989 := 2^7 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 8^4 + 9^2$	$24236 := -2^2 + 4^7 - 2^0 + 3^4 + 6^5$
$23907 := 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 7^5$	$24032 := -2^1 + 4^6 - 0^0 + 3^9 + 2^8$	$24243 := -2^5 - 4^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 3^9$
$23908 := 2^7 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 8^4$	$24034 := -2^1 + 4^4 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^6$	$24245 := 2^7 + 4^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5$
$23924 := 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^1 + 2^7 + 4^6$	$24034 := 2^6 + 4^5 + 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^7$	$24263 := -2^4 + 4^7 + 2^7 + 6^5 - 3^2$
$23924 := -2^6 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 2^7 + 4^6$	$24036 := -2^7 + 4^7 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 6^5$	$24264 := 2^3 + 4^3 + 2^5 + 6^5 + 4^7$
$23925 := -2^9 + 3^7 + 9^4 + 2^6 + 5^6$	$24036 := 2^8 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 6^0$	$24264 := -2^3 - 4^2 + 2^7 + 6^5 + 4^7$
$23928 := 2^2 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 2^6 + 8^4$	$24037 := 2^8 + 4^6 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 7^0$	$24265 := -2^2 + 4^7 - 2^4 + 6^5 + 5^3$
$23930 := -2^7 - 3^7 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 0^0$	$24038 := 2^1 + 4^4 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 8^4$	$24265 := 2^4 + 4^7 + 2^6 + 6^5 + 5^2$
$23943 := 2^1 + 3^4 + 9^2 + 4^6 + 3^9$	$24043 := 2^3 + 4^4 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 3^9$	$24266 := -2^4 + 4^7 + 2^7 + 6^5 - 6^1$
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$23945 := 2^5 + 3^9 + 9^1 + 4^6 + 5^3$	$24063 := -2^4 + 4^7 + 0^1 + 6^5 - 3^4$	$24269 := -2^2 + 4^7 + 2^5 + 6^4 + 9^4$
$23947 := 2^7 + 3^7 + 9^3 + 4^6 + 7^5$	$24064 := -2^5 - 4^3 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 4^7$	$24283 := -2^2 - 4^1 + 2^9 + 8^4 + 3^9$
$23947 := -2^8 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 4^6 + 7^3$	$24067 := -2^9 - 4^1 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 7^5$	$24286 := -2^1 + 4^7 + 2^6 + 8^2 + 6^5$
$23948 := -2^3 - 3^7 - 9^4 - 4^3 + 8^5$	$24076 := -2^9 + 4^1 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 6^5$	$24288 := -2^5 - 4^6 - 2^8 - 8^4 + 8^5$
$23949 := 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 4^6 + 9^2$	$24096 := -2^6 + 4^7 - 0^0 + 9^0 + 6^5$	$24293 := 2^9 + 4^6 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 3^9$
$23963 := -2^8 - 3^6 + 9^4 - 6^4 + 3^9$	$24136 := -2^5 + 4^7 - 1^0 + 3^2 + 6^5$	$24306 := 2^6 + 4^7 + 3^4 + 0^0 + 6^5$
		$24308 := 2^4 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 8^3$
		$24316 := 2^7 + 4^7 + 3^3 + 1^0 + 6^5$
		$24324 := 2^5 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 4^6$

$24332 := 2^5 + 4^6 + 3^2 + 3^9 + 2^9$	$24395 := -2^8 - 4^6 + 3^8 + 9^4 + 5^6$	$24533 := 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 3^0 + 3^9$
$24333 := -2^1 - 4^6 + 3^7 + 3^8 + 3^9$	$24396 := -2^3 + 4^7 + 3^5 + 9^0 + 6^5$	$24534 := -2^2 + 4^6 - 5^6 + 3^9 + 4^7$
$24334 := 2^9 + 4^2 + 3^3 + 3^9 + 4^6$	$24396 := 2^7 + 4^7 + 3^3 + 9^2 + 6^5$	$24536 := 2^3 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 3^5 + 6^5$
$24336 := -2^3 - 4^9 - 3^2 + 3^8 + 6^7$	$24397 := 2^1 + 4^5 + 3^1 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$24538 := -2^3 + 4^6 + 5^6 + 3^6 + 8^4$
$24336 := 2^9 + 4^6 + 3^2 + 3^9 + 6^2$	$24397 := -2^2 + 4^5 + 3^2 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$24567 := -2^4 + 4^0 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^5$
$24337 := 2^1 + 4^3 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 7^4$	$24399 := -2^2 + 4^7 + 3^6 + 9^3 + 9^4$	$24572 := 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 2^9$
$24337 := -2^4 + 4^4 + 3^6 + 3^8 + 7^5$	$24423 := 2^7 + 4^1 + 4^6 + 2^9 + 3^9$	$24576 := -2^1 - 4^1 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 6^5$
$24339 := -2^6 + 4^7 + 3^6 + 3^6 + 9^4$	$24426 := 2^1 + 4^4 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 6^5$	$24576 := 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 6^2$
$24345 := 2^9 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^5$	$24436 := 2^5 + 4^0 + 4^7 + 3^5 + 6^5$	$24579 := -2^2 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 7^4 + 9^4$
$24346 := -2^3 - 4^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 6^7$	$24444 := -2^7 - 4^1 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 4^7$	$24593 := -2^1 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^4 + 3^9$
$24352 := 2^3 + 4^5 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 2^9$	$24445 := -2^8 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 5^3$	$24593 := 2^5 + 4^5 + 5^5 + 9^3 + 3^9$
$24352 := -2^6 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 2^9$	$24447 := -2^7 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 4^7 - 7^0$	$24607 := 2^3 + 4^2 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 7^5$
$24353 := -2^2 - 4^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 3^8$	$24448 := -2^6 - 4^3 - 4^6 - 4^6 + 8^5$	$24608 := -2^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 8^3$
$24353 := 2^9 + 4^5 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 3^9$	$24449 := -2^7 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 9^0$	$24617 := 2^5 + 4^0 + 6^5 + 1^0 + 7^5$
$24356 := -2^1 - 4^9 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 6^7$	$24463 := -2^2 + 4^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 3^5$	$24624 := -2^5 - 4^2 + 6^5 + 2^9 + 4^7$
$24358 := -2^8 - 4^6 - 3^9 + 5^6 + 8^5$	$24464 := -2^4 + 4^3 + 4^4 + 6^5 + 4^7$	$24627 := -2^2 + 4^2 + 6^5 + 2^5 + 7^5$
$24372 := -2^2 + 4^5 + 3^8 + 7^5 - 2^4$	$24464 := 2^5 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 6^5 + 4^7$	$24627 := 2^3 + 4^1 + 6^5 + 2^5 + 7^5$
$24372 := 2^5 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 2^9$	$24465 := -2^6 - 4^4 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 5^4$	$24632 := -2^8 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 3^6 - 2^0$
$24373 := 2^3 + 4^6 + 3^5 + 7^3 + 3^9$	$24467 := 2^1 + 4^4 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 7^2$	$24634 := -2^8 + 4^0 + 6^5 + 3^6 + 4^7$
$24373 := -2^4 + 4^5 - 3^1 + 7^5 + 3^8$	$24467 := -2^5 - 4^1 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$24643 := -2^4 + 4^4 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 3^5$
$24374 := -2^1 - 4^2 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 4^5$	$24468 := -2^9 - 4^2 + 4^1 - 6^5 + 8^5$	$24644 := 2^5 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 4^6 + 4^7$
$24375 := -2^4 + 4^5 + 3^8 + 7^5 - 5^0$	$24483 := 2^1 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 3^8$	$24645 := -2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 5^5$
$24375 := 2^7 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 7^3 + 5^3$	$24483 := -2^6 - 4^4 + 4^5 + 8^4 + 3^9$	$24647 := -2^1 + 4^7 - 6^5 + 4^7 - 7^3$
$24376 := -2^5 - 4^4 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^5$	$24487 := -2^8 - 4^4 + 4^6 + 8^4 + 7^5$	$24647 := 2^5 + 4^2 + 6^5 + 4^2 + 7^5$
$24376 := 2^7 + 4^7 + 3^4 + 7^1 + 6^5$	$24489 := 2^3 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 9^4$	$24648 := -2^3 - 4^2 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 8^3$
$24377 := -2^3 + 4^5 + 3^8 + 7^5 - 7^1$	$24489 := -2^9 - 4^4 - 4^5 - 8^5 + 9^5$	$24649 := -2^5 - 4^6 - 6^6 + 4^7 + 9^5$
$24378 := -2^8 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 7^3 + 8^3$	$24493 := -2^4 + 4^0 + 4^6 + 9^3 + 3^9$	$24653 := -2^8 + 4^0 - 6^6 + 5^7 - 3^8$
$24379 := -2^2 + 4^5 - 3^2 + 7^5 + 9^4$	$24532 := 2^6 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 3^9 + 2^6$	$24656 := -2^7 + 4^7 - 6^0 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$24379 := 2^8 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 7^3 + 9^0$	$24532 := -2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 3^9 + 2^8$	$24658 := -2^7 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 5^4 + 8^0$
		$24662 := -2^2 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 6^5 + 2^9$
		$24663 := -2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 6^5 - 3^6$
		$24664 := 2^5 + 4^4 + 6^3 + 6^5 + 4^7$

$24665 := -2^4 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 6^5 + 5^6$	$24737 := -2^2 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 3^9 + 7^4$	$24861 := -2^7 - 4^1 + 8^5 - 6^5 + 1^0$
$24667 := -2^4 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 6^5 + 7^5$	$24738 := -2^4 + 4^5 - 7^2 + 3^9 + 8^4$	$24862 := -2^1 - 4^3 + 8^5 - 6^5 - 2^6$
$24667 := 2^5 + 4^2 + 6^2 + 6^5 + 7^5$	$24739 := -2^7 + 4^5 - 7^4 + 3^9 + 9^4$	$24863 := -2^1 - 4^9 + 8^3 + 6^7 + 3^8$
$24668 := -2^5 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 6^5 + 8^5$	$24742 := -2^8 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 4^6 - 2^0$	$24864 := -2^6 - 4^3 - 8^5 - 6^5 + 4^8$
$24669 := -2^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$24744 := -2^8 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 4^6$	$24864 := 2^7 + 4^3 + 8^3 + 6^5 + 4^7$
$24673 := 2^3 + 4^0 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 3^8$	$24753 := -2^2 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 3^6$	$24865 := 2^4 + 4^7 + 8^2 + 6^5 + 5^4$
$24674 := 2^9 + 4^0 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 4^7$	$24756 := -2^4 + 4^3 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$24865 := -2^6 - 4^3 + 8^5 - 6^5 + 5^0$
$24675 := -2^5 - 4^0 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 5^3$	$24756 := 2^5 + 4^2 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$24866 := -2^7 + 4^0 + 8^5 + 6^0 - 6^5$
$24680 := 2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 0^1$	$24759 := 2^1 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 9^3$	$24867 := -2^7 - 4^1 + 8^5 - 6^5 + 7^1$
$24681 := 2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 1^0$	$24760 := 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 6^5 + 0^0$	$24868 := -2^7 - 4^1 + 8^1 - 6^5 + 8^5$
$24682 := 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^1 + 2^9$	$24763 := -2^6 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 3^5$	$24868 := 2^8 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 6^2 + 8^4$
$24683 := 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 3^2$	$24766 := -2^5 - 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^3 + 6^5$	$24869 := -2^2 - 4^7 + 8^6 - 6^7 + 9^5$
$24683 := -2^1 - 4^3 - 6^5 + 8^5 - 3^5$	$24773 := 2^5 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 7^4 + 3^9$	$24870 := -2^7 + 4^6 + 8^4 + 7^5 - 0^0$
$24684 := -2^2 + 4^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 4^7$	$24776 := -2^6 + 4^4 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 6^5$	$24872 := -2^7 + 4^6 + 8^4 + 7^5 + 2^0$
$24684 := 2^3 + 4^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 4^7$	$24776 := 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^2 + 7^5 + 6^5$	$24883 := 2^4 + 4^5 + 8^2 + 8^4 + 3^9$
$24685 := 2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 5^1$	$24786 := -2^8 + 4^0 + 7^2 + 8^5 - 6^5$	$24887 := -2^5 - 4^6 - 8^4 + 8^5 + 7^3$
$24686 := 2^3 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 8^3 + 6^5$	$24796 := 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 + 6^5$	$24906 := 2^4 + 4^7 + 9^3 + 0^0 + 6^5$
$24687 := 2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 7^1$	$24796 := -2^9 - 4^1 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 6^5$	$24928 := -2^8 - 4^5 - 9^4 + 2^0 + 8^5$
$24687 := -2^9 + 4^4 - 6^5 + 8^5 - 7^2$	$24803 := 2^9 + 4^6 + 8^3 + 0^1 + 3^9$	$24932 := -2^5 - 4^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 - 2^8$
$24688 := 2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^1 + 8^3$	$24823 := 2^2 + 4^5 + 8^4 + 2^4 + 3^9$	$24936 := -2^3 - 4^1 + 9^4 + 3^9 - 6^4$
$24688 := -2^8 + 4^2 - 6^5 + 8^5 - 8^2$	$24824 := -2^3 + 4^6 + 8^4 + 2^8 + 4^7$	$24938 := -2^1 - 4^5 - 9^4 - 3^5 + 8^5$
$24689 := 2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 9^1$	$24828 := -2^2 - 4^6 - 8^4 + 2^8 + 8^5$	$24939 := -2^9 - 4^3 - 9^3 + 3^9 + 9^4$
$24689 := -2^3 - 4^5 - 6^5 + 8^5 + 9^3$	$24836 := 2^5 + 4^5 + 8^4 + 3^9 + 6^0$	$24952 := -2^9 + 4^7 - 9^4 + 5^6 + 2^4$
$24693 := -2^8 + 4^0 - 6^4 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$24836 := -2^7 - 4^0 + 8^5 - 3^3 - 6^5$	$24956 := -2^4 + 4^3 - 9^4 + 5^7 - 6^6$
$24697 := 2^5 + 4^0 + 6^4 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$24843 := 2^5 + 4^5 + 8^1 + 4^6 + 3^9$	$24957 := -2^9 - 4^5 + 9^4 + 5^5 + 7^5$
$24716 := 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 6^5$	$24845 := 2^2 + 4^5 + 8^4 + 4^6 + 5^6$	$24963 := -2^8 - 4^5 + 9^4 - 6^0 + 3^9$
$24736 := 2^3 + 4^3 + 7^5 + 3^4 + 6^5$	$24845 := -2^5 - 4^6 - 8^5 - 4^7 + 5^7$	$24968 := -2^4 - 4^0 + 9^5 - 6^4 - 8^5$
$24736 := -2^9 - 4^3 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 6^5$	$24848 := 2^4 + 4^4 + 8^4 + 4^7 + 8^4$	$24974 := -2^4 + 4^6 - 9^1 + 7^5 + 4^6$
$24737 := 2^1 + 4^5 + 7^3 + 3^8 + 7^5$	$24860 := -2^7 - 4^1 + 8^5 - 6^5 + 0^1$	$24976 := 2^7 + 4^4 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 6^5$
		$24976 := -2^7 - 4^6 + 9^5 + 7^5 - 6^6$
		$24986 := -2^2 - 4^0 - 9^0 + 8^5 - 6^5$
		$24996 := 2^1 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 6^5$

$25086 := -2^5 + 5^3 + 0^0 + 8^5 - 6^5$	$25476 := 2^9 + 5^3 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 6^5$	$25769 := -2^5 + 5^6 + 7^4 + 6^5 - 9^0$
$25237 := -2^2 + 5^5 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 7^4$	$25477 := -2^6 - 5^7 - 4^7 + 7^4 + 7^6$	$25784 := -2^9 + 5^2 - 7^4 + 8^5 - 4^6$
$25273 := 2^5 + 5^5 + 2^5 + 7^4 + 3^9$	$25479 := 2^3 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^4$	$25833 := -2^3 - 5^3 + 8^4 + 3^7 + 3^9$
$25273 := -2^6 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 7^4 + 3^9$	$25482 := -2^6 - 5^5 - 4^6 + 8^5 - 2^0$	$25834 := -2^2 - 5^4 + 8^5 - 3^8 + 4^4$
$25276 := 2^2 + 5^4 + 2^6 + 7^5 + 6^5$	$25484 := -2^6 - 5^5 + 4^0 + 8^5 - 4^6$	$25837 := -2^1 - 5^2 + 8^5 - 3^8 - 7^3$
$25295 := -2^3 + 5^5 - 2^3 + 9^4 + 5^6$	$25494 := -2^9 + 5^5 - 4^3 + 9^4 + 4^7$	$25838 := -2^8 - 5^4 + 8^3 - 3^8 + 8^5$
$25324 := -2^7 + 5^6 - 3^8 + 2^2 + 4^7$	$25547 := 2^9 + 5^5 + 5^5 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$25853 := -2^4 + 5^5 - 8^2 + 5^5 + 3^9$
$25325 := -2^1 + 5^5 + 3^8 + 2^4 + 5^6$	$25548 := -2^2 - 5^5 + 5^1 - 4^6 + 8^5$	$25856 := -2^1 + 5^6 - 8^4 + 5^6 - 6^4$
$25328 := -2^8 - 5^4 - 3^8 + 2^1 + 8^5$	$25583 := -2^1 - 5^5 + 5^6 + 8^5 - 3^9$	$25867 := 2^6 + 5^6 + 8^0 + 6^5 + 7^4$
$25345 := -2^7 + 5^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^6$	$25586 := -2^5 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 8^5 - 6^5$	$25867 := -2^9 - 5^9 + 8^7 + 6^0 - 7^6$
$25347 := -2^2 + 5^1 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$25633 := -2^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 + 3^6 - 3^8$	$25874 := -2^4 - 5^5 + 8^5 + 7^3 - 4^6$
$25348 := -2^9 - 5^4 - 3^7 - 4^6 + 8^5$	$25636 := -2^4 - 5^2 - 6^4 - 3^9 + 6^6$	$25892 := -2^1 + 5^3 - 8^5 + 9^5 - 2^9$
$25363 := -2^8 - 5^4 - 3^6 + 6^6 - 3^9$	$25639 := -2^2 + 5^7 + 6^1 + 3^8 - 9^5$	$25893 := -2^9 + 5^3 - 8^5 + 9^5 - 3^0$
$25366 := 2^7 + 5^5 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 6^5$	$25653 := -2^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 5^6 + 3^7$	$25894 := -2^5 - 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^4 - 4^4$
$25369 := -2^8 - 5^4 + 3^9 + 6^1 + 9^4$	$25653 := 2^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 5^6 + 3^7$	$25895 := -2^8 - 5^1 - 8^5 + 9^5 - 5^3$
$25384 := -2^6 + 5^6 - 3^8 + 8^5 - 4^7$	$25672 := -2^1 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 - 2^7$	$25897 := -2^4 - 5^2 - 8^5 + 9^5 - 7^3$
$25389 := -2^6 - 5^2 - 3^6 + 8^5 - 9^4$	$25673 := -2^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 - 3^0$	$25899 := -2^8 - 5^3 - 8^5 - 9^0 + 9^5$
$25389 := 2^8 + 5^4 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 9^3$	$25674 := -2^6 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 - 4^3$	$25923 := -2^6 - 5^0 + 9^4 - 2^8 + 3^9$
$25418 := -2^7 - 5^5 - 4^6 - 1^0 + 8^5$	$25675 := -2^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 + 5^6$	$25927 := -2^3 + 5^6 - 9^4 + 2^6 + 7^5$
$25433 := -2^4 + 5^6 + 4^7 + 3^0 - 3^8$	$25689 := -2^9 - 5^1 - 6^0 + 8^5 - 9^4$	$25928 := -2^8 - 5^2 - 9^4 + 2^1 + 8^5$
$25435 := -2^3 - 5^1 + 4^7 - 3^8 + 5^6$	$25694 := -2^9 - 5^6 + 6^6 - 9^3 - 4^6$	$25941 := -2^7 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 4^7 - 1^0$
$25436 := -2^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 3^8 - 6^6$	$25723 := 2^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 + 2^9 + 3^9$	$25942 := -2^6 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 4^7 - 2^6$
$25437 := -2^5 + 5^5 - 4^5 + 3^8 + 7^5$	$25743 := -2^9 + 5^7 - 7^6 + 4^8 + 3^5$	$25943 := -2^7 + 5^5 + 9^0 + 4^7 + 3^8$
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$25443 := -2^2 + 5^6 - 4^0 + 4^7 - 3^8$	$25748 := -2^8 + 5^7 - 7^6 + 4^8 - 8^1$	$25947 := -2^6 + 5^7 - 9^0 + 4^8 - 7^6$
$25458 := -2^6 - 5^2 - 4^6 - 5^5 + 8^5$	$25749 := -2^8 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 4^7 - 9^4$	$25948 := -2^1 - 5^0 - 9^4 - 4^4 + 8^5$
$25473 := 2^1 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 3^8$	$25762 := -2^3 + 5^6 + 7^4 + 6^5 - 2^5$	$25963 := -2^6 - 5^0 + 9^4 - 6^3 + 3^9$
$25475 := -2^9 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 7^6 + 5^7$	$25764 := 2^5 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 4^5$	$25982 := -2^8 - 5^0 - 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^5$
$25476 := -2^6 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 7^5 - 6^5$	$25765 := -2^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 + 6^5 + 5^6$	$25983 := -2^7 - 5^3 + 9^4 - 8^1 + 3^9$
		$25984 := -2^4 - 5^2 + 9^5 - 8^5 - 4^4$
		$25986 := -2^2 - 5^0 - 9^4 + 8^5 - 6^3$
		$25987 := -2^1 + 5^3 - 9^4 + 8^5 - 7^3$

$26036 := -2^7 - 6^4 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 6^5$	$26342 := -2^2 + 6^5 + 3^7 + 4^7 - 2^0$	$26443 := 2^5 + 6^5 + 4^3 + 4^7 + 3^7$
$26138 := -2^5 - 6^2 - 1^0 - 3^8 + 8^5$	$26344 := -2^1 + 6^5 + 3^7 + 4^7 - 4^0$	$26449 := -2^4 - 6^6 + 4^5 + 4^8 + 9^4$
$26189 := -2^4 - 6^0 - 1^0 + 8^5 - 9^4$	$26345 := -2^2 + 6^6 - 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^4$	$26463 := -2^3 + 6^2 - 4^5 + 6^5 + 3^9$
$26193 := -2^4 - 6^2 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$26346 := -2^1 + 6^0 + 3^7 + 4^7 + 6^5$	$26464 := -2^4 + 6^4 + 4^5 + 6^5 + 4^7$
$26198 := -2^1 - 6^1 - 1^0 - 9^4 + 8^5$	$26353 := -2^4 + 6^6 - 3^6 + 5^3 - 3^9$	$26483 := -2^2 + 6^3 + 4^3 + 8^5 - 3^8$
$26233 := -2^1 - 6^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 3^9$	$26354 := 2^1 + 6^5 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 4^7$	$26483 := 2^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 8^1 + 3^7$
$26238 := -2^5 - 6^0 + 2^6 - 3^8 + 8^5$	$26358 := -2^7 + 6^6 - 3^9 + 5^2 - 8^3$	$26489 := -2^3 + 6^3 - 4^8 + 8^5 + 9^5$
$26239 := -2^1 - 6^0 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 9^4$	$26359 := -2^2 - 6^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^4$	$26493 := -2^3 + 6^0 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 3^9$
$26247 := 2^7 + 6^5 + 2^9 + 4^5 + 7^5$	$26364 := 2^4 + 6^0 + 3^7 + 6^5 + 4^7$	$26493 := 2^5 + 6^3 + 4^0 + 9^4 + 3^9$
$26268 := -2^2 - 6^5 - 2^4 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$26376 := -2^9 - 6^2 - 3^9 - 7^2 + 6^6$	$26525 := -2^1 + 6^5 + 5^5 + 2^0 + 5^6$
$26283 := -2^4 - 6^2 + 2^7 + 8^5 - 3^8$	$26379 := 2^7 + 6^1 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 9^4$	$26533 := 2^7 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 3^8 + 3^9$
$26286 := -2^2 + 6^4 + 2^1 + 8^5 - 6^5$	$26392 := -2^2 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 9^4 - 2^6$	$26535 := 2^3 + 6^5 + 5^5 + 3^0 + 5^6$
$26289 := -2^1 - 6^1 + 2^4 - 8^5 + 9^5$	$26393 := 2^5 + 6^2 + 3^4 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$26537 := 2^3 + 6^2 + 5^5 + 3^8 + 7^5$
$26293 := 2^4 + 6^0 + 2^5 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$26393 := -2^6 + 6^3 - 3^1 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$26538 := -2^4 - 6^5 - 5^4 + 3^7 + 8^5$
$26293 := -2^4 + 6^0 + 2^6 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$26394 := -2^1 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 9^4 - 4^3$	$26555 := 2^2 + 6^5 + 5^2 + 5^5 + 5^6$
$26298 := -2^4 + 6^0 + 2^5 + 9^5 - 8^5$	$26394 := 2^7 + 6^1 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 4^2$	$26558 := -2^5 + 6^5 + 5^5 + 5^6 + 8^2$
$26309 := 2^6 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 9^4$	$26395 := -2^6 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 9^4 - 5^0$	$26559 := 2^5 + 6^5 + 5^5 + 5^6 + 9^0$
$26313 := 2^5 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 3^9$	$26397 := -2^6 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 7^0$	$26574 := 2^3 + 6^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 + 4^7$
$26328 := -2^3 + 6^0 - 3^8 + 2^7 + 8^5$	$26398 := -2^4 - 6^2 + 3^5 - 9^4 + 8^5$	$26579 := -2^1 - 6^2 - 5^6 - 7^5 + 9^5$
$26331 := -2^7 + 6^3 + 3^8 + 3^9 - 1^0$	$26403 := -2^5 + 6^5 - 4^5 + 0^1 + 3^9$	$26593 := 2^3 + 6^3 + 5^3 + 9^4 + 3^9$
$26332 := -2^2 - 6^2 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 2^7$	$26423 := -2^4 + 6^5 - 4^5 + 2^2 + 3^9$	$26593 := -2^8 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 9^0 - 3^9$
$26333 := 2^1 + 6^1 + 3^4 + 3^8 + 3^9$	$26424 := -2^3 + 6^6 - 4^6 + 2^8 - 4^7$	$26597 := -2^7 + 6^6 - 5^5 + 9^0 - 7^5$
$26333 := -2^7 + 6^3 + 3^0 + 3^8 + 3^9$	$26425 := -2^9 + 6^6 - 4^6 + 2^1 - 5^6$	$26624 := -2^4 - 6^6 + 6^5 - 2^4 + 4^8$
$26334 := -2^2 + 6^5 - 3^2 + 3^7 + 4^7$	$26428 := -2^2 + 6^6 - 4^7 + 2^8 - 8^4$	$26630 := -2^7 - 6^3 + 6^6 - 3^9 + 0^0$
$26335 := -2^4 + 6^6 - 3^9 + 3^1 - 5^4$	$26430 := -2^2 + 6^5 - 4^5 + 3^9 - 0^0$	$26640 := -2^4 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 + 0^1$
$26337 := 2^3 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 7^2$	$26432 := -2^1 + 6^5 - 4^5 + 3^9 - 2^0$	$26641 := -2^4 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 + 1^0$
$26337 := -2^8 + 6^1 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 7^3$	$26434 := -2^1 + 6^5 + 4^0 + 3^9 - 4^5$	$26642 := -2^4 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 + 2^1$
$26339 := 2^3 + 6^1 + 3^4 + 3^9 + 9^4$	$26437 := 2^8 + 6^0 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 7^4$	$26643 := -2^2 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 - 3^2$
$26340 := -2^3 + 6^5 + 3^7 + 4^7 + 0^0$	$26443 := -2^3 + 6^5 - 4^5 + 4^2 + 3^9$	$26644 := -2^3 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 - 4^1$
		$26645 := -2^4 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 + 5^1$
		$26646 := -2^2 - 6^1 + 6^5 + 4^8 - 6^6$
		$26647 := -2^1 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 - 7^1$

$26647 := 2^9 + 6^4 + 6^5 + 4^4 + 7^5$	$26934 := -2^9 + 6^5 - 9^1 + 3^9 - 4^1$	$27386 := -2^1 - 7^1 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 6^5$
$26648 := -2^4 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 + 8^1$	$26936 := -2^1 - 6^2 + 9^0 - 3^9 + 6^6$	$27431 := -2^5 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 3^8 - 1^0$
$26649 := -2^3 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 4^8 + 9^0$	$26937 := -2^9 + 6^5 - 9^1 + 3^9 - 7^0$	$27432 := -2^4 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 3^8 - 2^4$
$26655 := 2^7 + 6^0 + 6^5 + 5^5 + 5^6$	$26938 := -2^2 + 6^1 - 9^4 + 3^6 + 8^5$	$27433 := -2^2 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 3^8 - 3^3$
$26732 := -2^7 + 6^5 - 7^3 + 3^9 - 2^8$	$26939 := -2^9 + 6^5 + 9^0 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$27435 := -2^2 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 3^8 - 5^2$
$26733 := -2^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 + 3^9 - 3^6$	$26943 := -2^5 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 4^0 - 3^9$	$27436 := -2^3 + 7^0 - 4^2 + 3^9 + 6^5$
$26734 := -2^5 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 3^7 - 4^1$	$26953 := -2^4 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 5^1 - 3^9$	$27439 := -2^4 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 3^8 - 9^1$
$26735 := -2^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 + 3^3 - 5^5$	$26963 := -2^1 + 6^0 - 9^1 + 6^6 - 3^9$	$27449 := -2^4 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 4^6 + 9^4$
$26736 := 2^7 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 6^5$	$26973 := -2^1 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 7^0 - 3^9$	$27453 := -2^4 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 3^8$
$26737 := -2^5 + 6^5 - 7^0 + 3^7 + 7^5$	$26973 := 2^9 + 6^3 + 9^4 + 7^0 + 3^9$	$27455 := -2^8 + 7^5 - 4^6 + 5^6 - 5^4$
$26738 := -2^4 + 6^7 + 7^4 + 3^8 - 8^6$	$26975 := -2^2 + 6^5 - 9^3 + 7^5 + 5^5$	$27456 := -2^8 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^5$
$26739 := -2^5 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 3^7 + 9^0$	$26977 := -2^3 + 6^5 + 9^0 + 7^4 + 7^5$	$27458 := -2^5 - 7^5 - 4^6 + 5^6 + 8^5$
$26753 := -2^1 + 6^6 - 7^3 + 5^3 - 3^9$	$26993 := -2^4 + 6^2 + 9^3 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$27463 := 2^1 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 6^5 + 3^9$
$26763 := -2^3 + 6^0 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 3^7$	$27236 := -2^3 - 7^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 6^5$	$27463 := -2^1 + 7^1 - 4^0 + 6^5 + 3^9$
$26773 := 2^1 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 3^7$	$27258 := -2^4 - 7^4 + 2^5 - 5^5 + 8^5$	$27469 := 2^2 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4$
$26773 := -2^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 + 7^5 + 3^7$	$27326 := -2^2 - 7^0 + 3^9 - 2^7 + 6^5$	$27473 := 2^1 + 7^1 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 3^8$
$26777 := -2^8 + 6^5 + 7^2 + 7^4 + 7^5$	$27343 := -2^4 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 3^8$	$27479 := 2^3 + 7^1 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 9^4$
$26778 := -2^5 - 6^2 - 7^6 - 7^6 + 8^6$	$27346 := -2^7 - 7^0 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^5$	$27492 := -2^2 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 2^5$
$26793 := 2^9 + 6^2 + 7^0 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$27346 := 2^9 + 7^5 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 6^5$	$27493 := 2^1 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 3^3$
$26797 := -2^1 - 6^6 - 7^4 + 9^5 + 7^5$	$27349 := 2^5 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 9^4$	$27493 := -2^7 + 7^4 - 4^5 + 9^4 + 3^9$
$26823 := -2^7 + 6^5 - 8^3 + 2^2 + 3^9$	$27362 := -2^4 - 7^2 + 3^9 + 6^5 - 2^5$	$27496 := -2^2 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 6^2$
$26836 := -2^7 - 6^0 - 8^1 - 3^9 + 6^6$	$27363 := -2^3 - 7^1 - 3^4 + 6^5 + 3^9$	$27497 := -2^4 + 7^2 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 7^5$
$26843 := -2^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 4^7 + 3^7$	$27363 := 2^9 + 7^5 + 3^4 + 6^5 + 3^7$	$27497 := 2^5 + 7^0 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 7^5$
$26845 := -2^1 - 6^8 + 8^7 - 4^3 - 5^8$	$27364 := -2^3 - 7^3 + 3^9 + 6^5 + 4^4$	$27549 := 2^5 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 4^5 + 9^4$
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$26883 := -2^7 + 6^5 - 8^3 + 8^2 + 3^9$	$27369 := -2^1 - 7^1 + 3^9 + 6^5 - 9^2$	$27568 := -2^1 + 7^5 - 5^5 + 6^6 - 8^5$
$26932 := -2^4 + 6^5 + 9^0 + 3^9 - 2^9$	$27384 := -2^4 + 7^5 + 3^8 + 8^4 - 4^3$	$27568 := 2^6 + 7^1 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 8^4$
$26933 := -2^2 - 6^2 + 9^3 + 3^8 + 3^9$	$27385 := -2^2 + 7^5 - 3^8 + 8^5 - 5^6$	$27569 := -2^2 - 7^1 - 5^7 + 6^6 + 9^5$
		$27584 := -2^9 + 7^2 - 5^4 + 8^5 - 4^6$
		$27614 := -2^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 1^0 - 4^7$
		$27630 := -2^5 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^7 + 0^1$

$27631 := -2^5 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^7 + 1^0$	$27818 := -2^9 - 7^3 - 8^4 + 1^0 + 8^5$	$28289 := -2^7 - 8^4 - 2^8 + 8^5 + 9^0$
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$27637 := 2^7 + 7^0 + 6^5 + 3^9 + 7^2$	$27894 := -2^3 - 7^4 + 8^5 - 9^4 + 4^6$	$28337 := -2^3 + 8^5 - 3^8 + 3^7 - 7^2$
$27638 := -2^4 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^7 - 8^1$	$27898 := -2^2 - 7^4 + 8^4 - 9^4 + 8^5$	$28338 := -2^6 + 8^1 - 3^8 + 3^7 + 8^5$
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$27652 := -2^6 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 5^5 + 2^3$	$27965 := 2^8 + 7^5 + 9^0 + 6^5 + 5^5$	$28357 := -2^8 + 8^5 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^4$
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$27656 := -2^4 + 7^5 - 6^2 + 5^5 + 6^5$	$27984 := 2^3 + 7^5 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 4^6$	$28374 := -2^9 + 8^5 - 3^7 + 7^4 - 4^6$
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$27658 := -2^4 - 7^6 + 6^4 - 5^9 + 8^7$	$28036 := 2^6 + 8^3 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 6^5$	$28376 := -2^4 + 8^5 - 3^8 + 7^4 - 6^3$
$27659 := -2^4 - 7^3 - 6^6 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$28139 := -2^8 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 3^7 - 9^4$	$28378 := -2^1 - 8^4 - 3^5 - 7^2 + 8^5$
$27672 := -2^5 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 + 2^8$	$28158 := -2^9 - 8^4 - 1^0 - 5^0 + 8^5$	$28379 := -2^4 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 7^0 - 9^4$
$27673 := -2^7 - 7^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 3^9$	$28224 := -2^6 + 8^5 - 2^9 + 2^7 - 4^6$	$28388 := -2^8 - 8^0 - 3^3 - 8^4 + 8^5$
$27675 := -2^5 - 7^0 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 5^5$	$28228 := -2^9 - 8^4 + 2^2 + 2^6 + 8^5$	$28388 := 2^9 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 8^4$
$27693 := -2^1 - 7^1 + 6^6 + 9^3 - 3^9$	$28246 := -2^1 + 8^4 - 2^3 + 4^7 + 6^5$	$28389 := -2^2 - 8^0 + 3^7 + 8^5 - 9^4$
$27696 := -2^7 - 7^5 - 6^4 - 9^3 + 6^6$	$28264 := 2^2 + 8^4 + 2^2 + 6^5 + 4^7$	$28393 := -2^1 + 8^5 - 3^7 + 9^0 - 3^7$
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$27749 := 2^1 + 7^4 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 9^4$	$28284 := -2^2 - 8^3 + 2^7 + 8^5 - 4^6$	$28399 := -2^2 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 9^1 - 9^4$
$27763 := -2^5 - 7^1 + 7^3 + 6^5 + 3^9$	$28285 := -2^8 - 8^4 - 2^8 + 8^5 + 5^3$	$28403 := -2^9 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 0^1 + 3^5$
$27765 := 2^3 + 7^2 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 5^5$	$28287 := -2^7 - 8^4 - 2^8 + 8^5 - 7^0$	$28408 := -2^3 - 8^4 - 4^4 + 0^1 + 8^5$
$27767 := -2^6 - 7^5 - 7^6 + 6^7 - 7^6$	$28288 := -2^6 - 8^2 - 2^8 - 8^4 + 8^5$	$28416 := -2^8 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 1^0 - 6^0$
		$28418 := -2^8 + 8^0 - 4^6 + 1^0 + 8^5$
		$28420 := -2^8 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 2^2 + 0^1$
		$28421 := -2^8 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 2^2 + 1^0$

$28422 := -2^1 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 2^3 - 2^8$	$28518 := -2^7 - 8^4 - 5^2 - 1^0 + 8^5$	$28648 := -2^1 - 8^4 - 6^1 - 4^2 + 8^5$
$28423 := -2^3 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 2^1 - 3^5$	$28533 := 2^6 + 8^4 + 5^6 + 3^7 + 3^8$	$28649 := -2^6 - 8^2 - 6^6 + 4^7 + 9^5$
$28424 := -2^3 + 8^5 - 4^4 + 2^4 - 4^6$	$28534 := -2^4 + 8^5 - 5^3 + 3^1 - 4^6$	$28658 := -2^3 - 8^4 - 6^0 - 5^1 + 8^5$
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$28443 := -2^1 + 8^5 - 4^5 + 4^7 - 3^9$	$28548 := -2^7 - 8^0 + 5^1 - 4^6 + 8^5$	$28674 := -2^2 - 8^0 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 4^6$
$28445 := -2^4 - 8^3 + 4^7 - 4^8 + 5^7$	$28553 := -2^5 + 8^5 - 5^3 + 5^6 - 3^9$	$28676 := -2^1 + 8^4 - 6^0 + 7^5 + 6^5$
$28448 := -2^5 - 8^4 + 4^3 - 4^4 + 8^5$	$28554 := -2^7 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 5^1 - 4^6$	$28678 := -2^1 + 8^0 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 8^4$
$28453 := -2^8 + 8^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 3^9$	$28558 := -2^6 - 8^4 - 5^2 - 5^2 + 8^5$	$28679 := -2^1 - 8^5 - 6^0 + 7^4 + 9^5$
$28463 := -2^1 + 8^5 - 4^6 + 6^2 - 3^5$	$28567 := -2^6 + 8^0 - 5^6 + 6^6 - 7^4$	$28682 := -2^2 - 8^4 + 6^1 + 8^5 + 2^3$
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$28479 := -2^7 + 8^5 - 4^0 + 7^4 - 9^4$	$28576 := -2^7 + 8^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 6^5$	$28686 := -2^4 - 8^4 - 6^1 + 8^5 + 6^2$
$28480 := -2^7 - 8^2 - 4^6 + 8^5 + 0^1$	$28579 := -2^2 + 8^5 - 5^2 + 7^4 - 9^4$	$28714 := -2^3 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 1^0 - 4^6$
$28481 := -2^7 - 8^2 - 4^6 + 8^5 + 1^0$	$28582 := -2^6 - 8^4 - 5^2 + 8^5 - 2^0$	$28718 := -2^1 - 8^4 + 7^2 - 1^0 + 8^5$
$28482 := -2^7 - 8^2 - 4^6 + 8^5 + 2^1$	$28583 := -2^7 + 8^0 + 5^6 + 8^5 - 3^9$	$28733 := -2^2 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 3^7 - 3^8$
$28483 := -2^7 - 8^2 - 4^6 + 8^5 + 3^1$	$28584 := -2^6 + 8^0 - 5^2 + 8^5 - 4^6$	$28738 := -2^3 - 8^4 - 7^1 + 3^4 + 8^5$
$28484 := -2^7 - 8^2 + 4^1 + 8^5 - 4^6$	$28598 := -2^6 - 8^4 - 5^0 - 9^1 + 8^5$	$28758 := -2^5 - 8^4 - 7^1 + 5^3 + 8^5$
$28485 := -2^7 - 8^2 - 4^6 + 8^5 + 5^1$	$28604 := -2^5 + 8^5 - 6^2 + 0^1 - 4^6$	$28773 := -2^4 - 8^4 + 7^5 + 7^5 - 3^6$
$28486 := -2^7 - 8^2 - 4^6 + 8^5 + 6^1$	$28608 := -2^6 - 8^4 - 6^0 + 0^0 + 8^5$	$28775 := -2^2 + 8^7 - 7^6 + 7^4 - 5^9$
$28487 := -2^4 - 8^3 - 4^6 + 8^5 + 7^3$	$28624 := -2^4 + 8^5 - 6^2 + 2^2 - 4^6$	$28776 := -2^9 - 8^3 - 7^2 - 7^5 + 6^6$
$28488 := -2^7 + 8^1 - 4^3 + 8^5 - 8^4$	$28625 := -2^2 + 8^5 - 6^5 + 2^9 + 5^5$	$28794 := -2^3 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 9^2 - 4^6$
$28489 := -2^3 - 8^4 - 4^4 + 8^5 + 9^2$	$28628 := -2^2 - 8^4 - 6^2 - 2^2 + 8^5$	$28795 := -2^9 - 8^5 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 5^4$
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$28498 := -2^8 + 8^0 - 4^6 + 9^2 + 8^5$	$28638 := -2^3 - 8^4 + 6^0 - 3^3 + 8^5$	$28823 := -2^2 - 8^4 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 3^3$
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		$28826 := -2^6 - 8^4 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 6^3$
		$28843 := -2^2 - 8^4 + 8^5 + 4^4 - 3^4$
		$28845 := -2^4 - 8^4 + 8^5 + 4^3 + 5^3$

$28847 := -2^5 - 8^4 + 8^5 + 4^4 - 7^2$	$29433 := -2^6 - 9^1 + 4^7 + 3^8 + 3^8$	$29580 := -2^6 + 9^0 - 5^5 + 8^5 + 0^1$
$28848 := -2^4 - 8^2 - 8^4 + 4^4 + 8^5$	$29434 := -2^3 + 9^4 - 4^3 + 3^8 + 4^7$	$29581 := -2^6 + 9^0 - 5^5 + 8^5 + 1^0$
$28863 := -2^4 - 8^4 + 8^5 - 6^2 + 3^5$	$29435 := 2^1 + 9^4 + 4^3 + 3^9 + 5^5$	$29582 := -2^6 + 9^0 - 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^1$
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$28958 := -2^9 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 5^5 - 8^5$	$29473 := -2^5 - 9^4 + 4^7 - 7^0 + 3^9$	$29589 := -2^6 + 9^0 - 5^5 + 8^5 + 9^1$
$28973 := -2^8 - 8^6 - 9^6 + 7^7 - 3^6$	$29474 := 2^5 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 7^4 + 4^7$	$29633 := -2^2 - 9^1 + 6^5 + 3^7 + 3^9$
$28974 := -2^5 + 8^5 - 9^1 + 7^3 - 4^6$	$29475 := -2^1 + 9^2 - 4^8 + 7^5 + 5^7$	$29637 := -2^7 - 9^2 + 6^6 - 3^1 - 7^5$
$28994 := -2^9 + 8^5 + 9^4 + 9^4 - 4^7$	$29477 := -2^5 - 9^1 - 4^6 + 7^5 + 7^5$	$29654 := -2^9 - 9^2 + 6^6 - 5^2 - 4^7$
$29234 := -2^4 + 9^4 - 2^8 + 3^8 + 4^7$	$29490 := -2^4 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 0^1$	$29657 := -2^8 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 5^6 - 7^2$
$29249 := -2^8 + 9^4 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 9^4$	$29491 := -2^4 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 1^0$	$29672 := -2^5 - 9^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 - 2^6$
$29258 := -2^7 - 9^0 - 2^8 - 5^5 + 8^5$	$29492 := -2^4 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 2^1$	$29673 := -2^8 - 9^0 + 6^6 - 7^5 + 3^4$
$29259 := 2^8 + 9^4 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 9^4$	$29493 := -2^2 - 9^1 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 3^8$	$29676 := -2^7 - 9^1 - 6^2 - 7^5 + 6^6$
$29305 := -2^6 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 5^5$	$29494 := -2^3 + 9^4 - 4^1 + 9^4 + 4^7$	$29678 := -2^6 - 9^6 - 6^3 + 7^7 - 8^6$
$29348 := -2^7 - 9^2 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 8^5$	$29495 := -2^4 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 5^1$	$29679 := -2^3 - 9^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 - 9^2$
$29352 := -2^4 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 5^5 - 2^0$	$29496 := -2^2 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 9^4 - 6^1$	$29697 := -2^4 + 9^4 - 6^3 + 9^4 + 7^5$
$29354 := -2^4 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 4^0$	$29497 := -2^1 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 9^4 - 7^1$	$29726 := -2^7 + 9^0 - 7^5 + 2^2 + 6^6$
$29365 := -2^2 - 9^3 - 3^9 + 6^6 + 5^5$	$29498 := -2^3 + 9^4 - 4^7 + 9^4 + 8^5$	$29743 := -2^5 + 9^3 - 7^5 + 4^8 - 3^9$
$29367 := -2^3 + 9^0 - 3^9 + 6^6 + 7^4$	$29499 := -2^3 + 9^0 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 9^4$	$29746 := -2^7 + 9^1 - 7^5 + 4^2 + 6^6$
$29384 := -2^2 - 9^2 - 3^9 + 8^5 + 4^7$	$29528 := -2^1 - 9^2 - 5^5 - 2^5 + 8^5$	$29749 := -2^7 - 9^2 + 7^7 - 4^9 - 9^6$
$29385 := 2^3 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 8^1 + 5^5$	$29543 := 2^5 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 4^7 + 3^8$	$29760 := -2^3 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^6 + 0^1$
$29385 := -2^4 + 9^0 - 3^5 + 8^5 - 5^5$	$29546 := -2^1 - 9^3 + 5^1 - 4^7 + 6^6$	$29761 := -2^3 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^6 + 1^0$
$29387 := -2^3 - 9^3 - 3^5 + 8^5 - 7^4$	$29564 := -2^1 - 9^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 4^7$	$29762 := -2^1 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 2^2$
$29388 := -2^2 - 9^1 + 3^6 - 8^4 + 8^5$	$29567 := -2^8 - 9^0 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5$	$29763 := -2^1 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^1$
$29416 := -2^7 - 9^3 - 4^7 + 1^0 + 6^6$	$29569 := -2^2 - 9^3 - 5^6 + 6^6 - 9^3$	$29764 := -2^3 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^6 + 4^1$
		$29765 := -2^1 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 5^0$
		$29766 := -2^3 - 9^2 - 7^5 + 6^1 + 6^6$
		$29767 := -2^1 - 9^2 + 7^0 + 6^6 - 7^5$

$29768 := -2^3 - 9^1 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 8^2$	$30246 := -3^2 - 0^0 - 2^4 - 4^7 + 6^6$	$30558 := -3^7 + 0^0 - 5^2 + 5^0 + 8^5$
$29769 := -2^3 + 9^1 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 9^2$	$30264 := -3^1 - 0^0 - 2^2 + 6^6 - 4^7$	$30578 := -3^7 - 0^0 - 5^0 - 7^0 + 8^5$
$29782 := -2^6 - 9^1 - 7^4 + 8^5 - 2^9$	$30278 := -3^4 + 0^1 - 2^3 - 7^4 + 8^5$	$30580 := -3^7 + 0^0 - 5^0 + 8^5 - 0^0$
$29783 := -2^8 - 9^6 + 7^7 - 8^6 + 3^4$	$30286 := -3^7 + 0^0 - 2^9 + 8^5 + 6^3$	$30580 := -3^7 - 0^0 - 5^0 + 8^5 + 0^0$
$29784 := -2^9 - 9^4 - 7^1 + 8^5 + 4^6$	$30287 := -3^4 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 8^5 - 7^4$	$30581 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 8^5 - 1^0$
$29786 := -2^7 + 9^0 - 7^5 + 8^2 + 6^6$	$30288 := -3^8 + 0^0 - 2^4 + 8^4 + 8^5$	$30582 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 8^5 - 2^0$
$29832 := -2^2 - 9^3 + 8^5 - 3^7 - 2^4$	$30328 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 3^1 - 2^8 + 8^5$	$30583 := -3^1 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 8^5 - 3^7$
$29833 := -2^4 - 9^3 + 8^5 - 3^1 - 3^7$	$30338 := -3^1 + 0^0 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 8^4$	$30584 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 8^5 + 4^0$
$29834 := -2^1 - 9^3 + 8^5 - 3^7 - 4^2$	$30340 := 3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 0^1$	$30585 := -3^6 + 0^1 + 5^6 + 8^2 + 5^6$
$29835 := -2^4 - 9^3 + 8^5 - 3^7 - 5^0$	$30341 := 3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 1^0$	$30586 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 8^5 - 6^0$
$29837 := -2^3 - 9^3 + 8^5 - 3^7 - 7^1$	$30342 := 3^8 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 2^0$	$30586 := 3^9 + 0^0 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 6^5$
$29839 := -2^2 - 9^1 + 8^5 - 3^7 - 9^3$	$30343 := 3^1 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 3^9$	$30587 := -3^7 + 0^1 - 5^0 + 8^5 + 7^1$
$29843 := -2^3 - 9^3 + 8^5 - 4^0 - 3^7$	$30344 := 3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 4^6$	$30588 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 8^5$
$29847 := -2^9 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 4^0 - 7^4$	$30345 := 3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 5^1$	$30589 := -3^7 + 0^1 - 5^0 + 8^5 + 9^1$
$29853 := -2^2 - 9^3 + 8^5 + 5^1 - 3^7$	$30346 := 3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^1$	$30618 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 1^0 + 8^5$
$29856 := -2^1 - 9^0 + 8^5 - 5^5 + 6^3$	$30347 := 3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 7^1$	$30654 := -3^5 + 0^1 + 6^6 + 5^4 - 4^7$
$29857 := -2^7 - 9^0 + 8^5 - 5^5 + 7^3$	$30348 := 3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 8^1$	$30659 := -3^4 + 0^1 - 6^6 + 5^7 - 9^3$
$29859 := -2^9 - 9^0 + 8^5 - 5^5 + 9^3$	$30349 := 3^2 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 9^4$	$30682 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 2^6$
$29867 := -2^6 + 9^2 + 8^0 + 6^6 - 7^5$	$30368 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 3^1 - 6^3 + 8^5$	$30694 := -3^3 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 9^4 + 4^7$
$29873 := -2^2 - 9^6 - 8^6 + 7^7 - 3^4$	$30384 := -3^8 + 0^1 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 4^6$	$30698 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 8^5$
$29877 := -2^5 - 9^6 - 8^6 - 7^2 + 7^7$	$30387 := -3^5 + 0^1 - 3^7 + 8^5 + 7^2$	$30758 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 5^6 + 8^3$
$29878 := -2^4 - 9^6 - 8^2 + 7^7 - 8^6$	$30446 := -3^4 - 0^0 + 4^4 - 4^7 + 6^6$	$30822 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 2^8 - 2^4$
$29927 := -2^2 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 2^1 + 7^5$	$30483 := -3^4 - 0^0 - 4^2 + 8^5 - 3^7$	$30823 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 2^0 + 3^5$
$29947 := 2^1 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 7^5$	$30486 := -3^6 - 0^0 - 4^4 + 8^5 - 6^4$	$30828 := -3^7 - 0^0 - 8^1 + 2^8 + 8^5$
$29947 := -2^1 - 9^1 - 9^6 - 4^9 + 7^7$	$30498 := -3^7 - 0^0 - 4^0 - 9^2 + 8^5$	$30829 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 2^8 - 9^1$
$29965 := 2^1 + 9^0 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 5^6$	$30525 := -3^6 + 0^1 + 5^6 + 2^2 + 5^6$	$30832 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 3^5 + 2^3$
$29965 := -2^8 - 9^2 - 9^3 + 6^6 - 5^6$	$30538 := -3^7 + 0^0 - 5^3 + 3^4 + 8^5$	$30833 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 3^5$
$29967 := 2^1 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 7^5$	$30552 := -3^6 - 0^0 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 2^5$	$30834 := -3^1 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 3^7 + 4^4$
$30245 := -3^9 + 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^8 - 5^6$	$30556 := -3^6 - 0^0 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$30842 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 2^8$
		$30857 := -3^6 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 5^6 - 7^5$
		$30862 := -3^7 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 2^6$
		$30867 := 3^7 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 + 7^5$

$30873 := -3^7 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 3^5$	$31868 := -3^7 - 1^0 - 8^1 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$32208 := -3^4 + 2^5 - 2^9 + 0^0 + 8^5$
$30935 := 3^7 + 0^0 + 9^4 + 3^8 + 5^6$	$31869 := -3^7 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 6^4 - 9^1$	$32228 := -3^3 - 2^0 - 2^8 - 2^8 + 8^5$
$30964 := 3^5 + 0^1 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 4^7$	$31886 := -3^6 - 1^0 + 8^2 + 8^5 - 6^3$	$32238 := -3^1 - 2^4 - 2^9 + 3^0 + 8^5$
$30965 := -3^9 + 0^1 + 9^5 - 6^5 - 5^4$	$31887 := -3^3 + 1^0 - 8^3 + 8^5 - 7^3$	$32248 := -3^1 - 2^0 - 2^9 - 4^1 + 8^5$
$30975 := -3^6 + 0^0 - 9^3 + 7^5 + 5^6$	$31956 := -3^5 + 1^0 + 9^3 + 5^7 - 6^6$	$32254 := -3^1 - 2^3 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 4^7$
$31068 := -3^9 - 1^0 + 0^1 + 6^6 + 8^4$	$31958 := -3^4 - 1^0 - 9^3 + 5^0 + 8^5$	$32254 := 3^5 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 4^7$
$31255 := 3^1 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 5^6$	$32008 := -3^6 - 2^5 + 0^0 + 0^1 + 8^5$	$32257 := -3^5 + 2^2 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 7^5$
$31283 := -3^5 - 1^0 - 2^9 + 8^5 - 3^6$	$32028 := -3^5 - 2^9 - 0^0 + 2^4 + 8^5$	$32258 := -3^1 + 2^2 - 2^9 + 5^0 + 8^5$
$31285 := -3^6 - 1^0 - 2^7 + 8^5 - 5^4$	$32038 := -3^6 - 2^0 + 0^0 - 3^0 + 8^5$	$32268 := -3^1 - 2^9 + 2^4 - 6^0 + 8^5$
$31308 := -3^6 - 1^0 - 3^6 - 0^0 + 8^5$	$32044 := -3^6 + 2^2 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 4^7$	$32275 := -3^3 - 2^1 - 2^7 + 7^5 + 5^6$
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$31558 := 3^5 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 8^2$	$32068 := 3^9 + 2^9 + 0^0 + 6^5 + 8^4$	$32287 := -3^2 - 2^0 - 2^7 + 8^5 - 7^3$
$31596 := -3^9 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 9^5 - 6^5$	$32078 := -3^6 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 8^5$	$32288 := -3^6 + 2^0 + 2^8 + 8^5 - 8^1$
$31645 := -3^4 + 1^0 - 6^6 + 4^4 + 5^7$	$32083 := -3^6 + 2^4 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 3^3$	$32293 := -3^8 - 2^8 - 2^8 + 9^5 - 3^9$
$31648 := -3^4 + 1^0 - 6^4 + 4^4 + 8^5$	$32085 := -3^3 - 2^5 + 0^0 + 8^5 - 5^4$	$32298 := -3^6 + 2^1 + 2^8 + 9^0 + 8^5$
$31685 := -3^5 + 1^0 - 6^3 + 8^5 - 5^4$	$32087 := -3^4 - 2^8 - 0^0 + 8^5 - 7^3$	$32308 := -3^5 + 2^9 - 3^6 + 0^1 + 8^5$
$31686 := -3^1 + 1^0 + 6^3 + 8^5 - 6^4$	$32088 := -3^6 - 2^4 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 8^5$	$32328 := -3^2 - 2^8 + 3^4 - 2^8 + 8^5$
$31687 := -3^7 + 1^0 - 6^4 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$32089 := -3^6 - 2^5 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 9^2$	$32344 := -3^7 - 2^9 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 4^7$
$31705 := -3^6 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 5^6$	$32168 := -3^4 - 2^9 - 1^0 - 6^1 + 8^5$	$32346 := -3^4 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^7 + 6^6$
$31734 := -3^7 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 4^7$	$32182 := -3^2 - 2^6 - 1^0 + 8^5 - 2^9$	$32347 := -3^4 - 2^1 - 3^9 - 4^8 + 7^6$
$31776 := -3^9 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 7^4 + 6^6$	$32183 := -3^4 - 2^9 - 1^0 + 8^5 + 3^2$	$32348 := -3^2 - 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 8^5$
$31823 := -3^6 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^9 - 3^6$	$32184 := -3^2 - 2^9 + 1^0 + 8^5 - 4^3$	$32358 := -3^3 - 2^0 + 3^5 - 5^4 + 8^5$
$31826 := -3^6 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 - 6^3$	$32187 := -3^5 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 8^5 - 7^3$	$32366 := -3^4 + 2^7 - 3^8 + 6^6 - 6^5$
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$31862 := -3^7 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 6^4 - 2^4$	$32189 := -3^5 - 2^8 + 1^0 + 8^5 - 9^2$	$32378 := -3^1 - 2^0 - 3^6 + 7^3 + 8^5$
		$32380 := -3^4 - 2^6 - 3^5 + 8^5 + 0^1$
		$32381 := -3^4 - 2^6 - 3^5 + 8^5 + 1^0$
		$32382 := -3^1 - 2^7 + 3^0 + 8^5 - 2^8$

$32383 := -3^3 + 2^7 - 3^5 + 8^5 - 3^5$	$32476 := -3^5 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^5 - 6^3$	$32564 := -3^1 + 2^9 - 5^6 + 6^6 + 4^5$
$32384 := -3^1 - 2^7 + 3^1 + 8^5 - 4^4$	$32477 := -3^4 - 2^5 - 4^5 + 7^5 + 7^5$	$32565 := 3^1 + 2^4 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 5^6$
$32385 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 8^5 - 5^4$	$32478 := -3^1 - 2^3 + 4^3 - 7^3 + 8^5$	$32568 := -3^5 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 8^5$
$32386 := -3^1 + 2^9 - 3^7 + 8^5 + 6^4$	$32479 := -3^6 + 2^3 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 9^1$	$32570 := 3^2 + 2^7 + 5^6 + 7^5 + 0^0$
$32387 := -3^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^4 + 7^5$	$32480 := -3^3 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 8^5 - 0^0$	$32578 := 3^4 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 7^5 + 8^2$
$32388 := -3^2 - 2^6 - 3^5 - 8^2 + 8^5$	$32482 := -3^3 + 2^0 - 4^1 + 8^5 - 2^8$	$32578 := -3^5 - 2^0 + 5^1 + 7^2 + 8^5$
$32389 := -3^2 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 8^5 + 9^0$	$32483 := -3^1 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 8^5 - 3^3$	$32581 := -3^5 + 2^5 + 5^2 + 8^5 - 1^0$
$32427 := -3^9 - 2^0 - 4^8 - 2^1 + 7^6$	$32484 := -3^3 - 2^0 - 4^4 - 8^5 + 4^8$	$32582 := -3^2 - 2^6 - 5^4 + 8^5 + 2^9$
$32428 := -3^4 - 2^0 - 4^4 - 2^1 + 8^5$	$32485 := -3^1 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 8^5 - 5^2$	$32583 := -3^1 - 2^6 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 3^5$
$32434 := -3^3 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 3^5 + 4^7$	$32486 := -3^1 + 2^0 - 4^3 + 8^5 - 6^3$	$32585 := -3^3 - 2^5 + 5^0 + 8^5 - 5^3$
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$32437 := -3^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 3^6 + 7^5$	$32488 := -3^2 - 2^4 - 4^4 + 8^0 + 8^5$	$32587 := -3^1 - 2^2 - 5^3 + 8^5 - 7^2$
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$32447 := -3^6 + 2^0 - 4^2 + 4^7 + 7^5$	$32498 := -3^1 - 2^1 - 4^4 - 9^1 + 8^5$	$32589 := -3^1 - 2^8 - 5^0 + 8^5 + 9^2$
$32448 := -3^4 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 4^2 + 8^5$	$32508 := -3^1 - 2^8 - 5^0 + 0^1 + 8^5$	$32608 := -3^2 + 2^6 - 6^3 + 0^0 + 8^5$
$32454 := -3^1 + 2^9 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 4^7$	$32518 := -3^5 - 2^0 - 5^1 - 1^0 + 8^5$	$32618 := -3^3 - 2^7 + 6^1 - 1^0 + 8^5$
$32455 := -3^5 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 5^6$	$32524 := 3^1 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 2^8 + 4^7$	$32628 := -3^1 - 2^3 - 6^0 - 2^7 + 8^5$
$32457 := -3^1 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 7^5$	$32527 := 3^3 + 2^2 + 5^6 + 2^6 + 7^5$	$32634 := -3^4 + 2^8 + 6^6 + 3^7 - 4^7$
$32458 := -3^3 - 2^1 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 8^5$	$32528 := -3^1 - 2^7 - 5^3 + 2^4 + 8^5$	$32638 := -3^1 + 2^3 - 6^3 + 3^4 + 8^5$
$32465 := -3^3 - 2^0 + 4^5 - 6^6 + 5^7$	$32538 := -3^5 - 2^0 + 5^1 + 3^2 + 8^5$	$32648 := -3^2 - 2^7 + 6^0 + 4^2 + 8^5$
$32467 := -3^6 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^5$	$32543 := -3^9 + 2^7 - 5^6 + 4^8 + 3^7$	$32653 := -3^8 - 2^8 + 6^6 - 5^4 - 3^8$
$32468 := -3^1 - 2^9 - 4^0 + 6^3 + 8^5$	$32545 := -3^4 - 2^3 + 5^4 + 4^7 + 5^6$	$32658 := -3^1 - 2^4 - 6^3 + 5^3 + 8^5$
$32470 := -3^6 + 2^3 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 0^1$	$32547 := -3^1 - 2^4 - 5^4 + 4^7 + 7^5$	$32668 := -3^2 - 2^7 + 6^0 + 6^2 + 8^5$
$32471 := -3^6 + 2^3 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 1^0$	$32548 := -3^1 - 2^7 - 5^2 - 4^3 + 8^5$	$32674 := -3^1 + 2^2 + 6^6 + 7^4 - 4^7$
$32472 := -3^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 2^3$	$32549 := 3^3 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 4^7 + 9^0$	$32677 := -3^6 + 2^3 - 6^3 + 7^5 + 7^5$
$32473 := -3^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 3^2$	$32554 := -3^4 + 2^0 + 5^4 + 5^6 + 4^7$	$32678 := -3^1 - 2^1 - 6^2 - 7^2 + 8^5$
$32474 := -3^5 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 4^7$	$32556 := 3^2 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$32679 := -3^8 - 2^9 + 6^6 - 7^3 - 9^4$
$32475 := -3^3 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 7^5 - 5^4$	$32556 := -3^2 + 2^0 - 5^7 + 5^8 - 6^7$	$32680 := -3^4 - 2^0 - 6^1 + 8^5 + 0^1$
		$32681 := -3^4 - 2^0 - 6^1 + 8^5 + 1^0$
		$32682 := -3^3 - 2^0 + 6^1 + 8^5 - 2^6$

$32683 := -3^1 - 2^1 + 6^0 + 8^5 - 3^4$	$32782 := -3^1 + 2^1 - 7^0 + 8^5 + 2^4$	$32806 := 3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 6^1$
$32684 := -3^1 - 2^4 - 6^0 + 8^5 - 4^3$	$32783 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 8^5 + 3^2$	$32807 := -3^1 - 2^3 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 7^2$
$32685 := -3^3 - 2^5 + 6^0 + 8^5 - 5^2$	$32783 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 3^2$	$32807 := 3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 7^1$
$32686 := -3^2 - 2^0 - 6^2 + 8^5 - 6^2$	$32784 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 8^5 + 4^2$	$32808 := -3^2 - 2^4 + 8^2 + 0^0 + 8^5$
$32687 := -3^1 - 2^7 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 7^2$	$32784 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 4^1$	$32808 := 3^3 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 0^0 + 8^5$
$32688 := -3^2 - 2^0 - 6^1 - 8^2 + 8^5$	$32785 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 5^1$	$32809 := -3^2 - 2^5 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 9^2$
$32689 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 6^1 + 8^5 - 9^2$	$32785 := -3^1 + 2^1 - 7^1 + 8^5 + 5^2$	$32809 := 3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 9^1$
$32694 := -3^7 - 2^3 - 6^5 + 9^5 - 4^7$	$32786 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 6^1$	$32810 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 0^1$
$32698 := -3^1 - 2^5 - 6^2 + 9^0 + 8^5$	$32786 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 6^1$	$32811 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 1^0$
$32708 := -3^1 - 2^3 - 7^2 + 0^1 + 8^5$	$32787 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 7^1$	$32812 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 - 1^0 + 2^6$
$32718 := -3^1 + 2^0 - 7^2 + 1^0 + 8^5$	$32787 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 7^1$	$32813 := 3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 3^2$
$32724 := -3^5 - 2^8 + 7^5 + 2^5 + 4^7$	$32788 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^1 + 8^5$	$32813 := -3^1 - 2^5 + 8^5 - 1^0 + 3^4$
$32725 := -3^3 + 2^6 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 5^6$	$32788 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 7^1 + 8^1 + 8^5$	$32814 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 4^3$
$32728 := -3^1 - 2^2 - 7^0 - 2^5 + 8^5$	$32789 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 9^1$	$32814 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 4^1$
$32738 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 7^0 - 3^3 + 8^5$	$32789 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 9^1$	$32815 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 5^1$
$32743 := 3^8 + 2^1 + 7^4 + 4^6 + 3^9$	$32798 := -3^1 + 2^0 - 7^2 + 9^2 + 8^5$	$32815 := -3^4 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 5^3$
$32744 := -3^2 - 2^3 - 7^1 + 4^7 + 4^7$	$32798 := 3^3 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 8^5$	$32816 := 3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 6^2$
$32748 := -3^1 - 2^1 + 7^0 - 4^2 + 8^5$	$32799 := -3^9 + 2^0 - 7^1 + 9^5 - 9^4$	$32817 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 7^2$
$32749 := 3^9 + 2^3 + 7^4 + 4^6 + 9^4$	$32800 := 3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 0^1$	$32817 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 7^1$
$32758 := -3^1 - 2^0 - 7^0 - 5^1 + 8^5$	$32801 := 3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 1^0$	$32818 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 1^0 + 8^5$
$32765 := -3^4 - 2^7 - 7^5 + 6^6 + 5^5$	$32802 := -3^1 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 2^5$	$32818 := -3^2 - 2^2 + 8^2 - 1^0 + 8^5$
$32768 := -3^1 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 8^5$	$32802 := 3^2 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 2^4$	$32819 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 9^1$
$32774 := -3^9 + 2^0 + 7^3 + 7^6 - 4^8$	$32803 := 3^1 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 3^3$	$32819 := -3^3 - 2^1 + 8^5 - 1^0 + 9^2$
$32778 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 8^5$	$32803 := -3^1 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 0^0 - 3^3$	$32820 := 3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 0^0$
$32780 := 3^1 + 2^0 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 0^0$	$32804 := 3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 4^2$	$32820 := -3^1 - 2^3 + 8^5 + 2^6 - 0^0$
$32780 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 0^1$	$32804 := -3^3 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 0^1 + 4^3$	$32821 := -3^2 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 2^6 - 1^0$
$32781 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 1^0$	$32805 := 3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 5^2$	$32822 := -3^1 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 2^6 - 2^3$
$32781 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 1^0$	$32805 := -3^1 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 0^0 - 5^2$	$32823 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 3^3$
$32782 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 8^5 + 2^3$	$32806 := -3^1 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 6^2$	$32824 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 8^5 - 2^2 + 4^3$
		$32825 := -3^1 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 2^6 - 5^1$
		$32825 := 3^3 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 2^2 + 5^2$

$32826 := -3^1 - 2^1 + 8^5 + 2^6 - 6^0$	$32842 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 2^5$	$32860 := -3^2 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 0^0$
$32826 := 3^2 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 6^0$	$32843 := -3^1 - 2^1 + 8^5 - 4^0 + 3^4$	$32860 := 3^3 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 0^1$
$32827 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 2^6 - 7^0$	$32843 := 3^2 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 4^3 + 3^0$	$32861 := 3^3 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 1^0$
$32828 := -3^1 - 2^0 - 8^2 + 2^7 + 8^5$	$32844 := 3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 4^3$	$32862 := -3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 2^6$
$32828 := 3^3 + 2^4 + 8^0 + 2^4 + 8^5$	$32844 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 4^3$	$32862 := 3^3 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 2^6$
$32829 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 8^5 - 2^4 + 9^2$	$32845 := -3^3 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 4^0 - 5^2$	$32863 := -3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 3^4$
$32829 := 3^3 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 9^0$	$32846 := -3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 4^3 + 6^0$	$32863 := 3^1 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 3^3$
$32830 := 3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 0^1$	$32846 := 3^2 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 4^3 + 6^0$	$32864 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 4^3$
$32830 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 3^4 + 0^1$	$32847 := -3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 7^2$	$32864 := 3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 4^3$
$32831 := 3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 1^0$	$32847 := 3^3 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 7^2$	$32865 := 3^3 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^1$
$32831 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 3^4 + 1^0$	$32849 := -3^1 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 9^2$	$32865 := -3^3 - 2^1 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^3$
$32832 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^0 + 2^6$	$32850 := -3^3 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 0^1$	$32866 := -3^1 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 6^2$
$32832 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 2^5$	$32851 := -3^2 - 2^5 + 8^5 + 5^3 - 1^0$	$32866 := 3^3 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 6^1$
$32833 := 3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 3^3$	$32852 := 3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 5^0 + 2^6$	$32867 := 3^3 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 7^1$
$32833 := -3^1 - 2^2 + 8^5 - 3^2 + 3^4$	$32852 := -3^1 - 2^1 + 8^5 + 5^2 + 2^6$	$32867 := -3^3 - 2^0 + 8^5 - 6^3 + 7^3$
$32834 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$32853 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 3^4$	$32868 := 3^1 + 2^5 + 8^2 + 6^0 + 8^5$
$32834 := 3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^1$	$32853 := 3^3 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 5^2 + 3^0$	$32868 := -3^5 + 2^7 - 8^0 + 6^3 + 8^5$
$32835 := 3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 5^1$	$32854 := -3^1 - 2^5 + 8^5 + 5^3 - 4^1$	$32869 := 3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 9^2$
$32835 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 3^4 + 5^1$	$32854 := 3^2 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 4^3$	$32869 := -3^3 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 6^0 - 9^0$
$32836 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 6^2$	$32855 := -3^1 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 5^0 + 5^2$	$32870 := -3^3 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 0^1$
$32836 := -3^1 - 2^2 + 8^5 + 3^4 - 6^1$	$32855 := 3^4 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 5^0 + 5^0$	$32871 := -3^2 + 2^6 + 8^5 + 7^2 - 1^0$
$32837 := 3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 7^2$	$32856 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 5^3 - 6^2$	$32872 := -3^2 - 2^3 + 8^5 - 7^1 + 2^7$
$32837 := -3^1 - 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^4 - 7^1$	$32856 := 3^4 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 6^0$	$32872 := 3^4 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 2^3$
$32838 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 8^2 + 3^0 + 8^5$	$32857 := -3^1 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 5^3 - 7^2$	$32873 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 7^3 - 3^5$
$32838 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 8^2 + 3^0 + 8^5$	$32857 := 3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 7^2$	$32873 := 3^2 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 3^4$
$32839 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^4 - 9^1$	$32858 := -3^1 + 2^2 + 8^2 + 5^2 + 8^5$	$32874 := 3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 4^3$
$32839 := 3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 9^1$	$32858 := 3^2 + 2^4 + 8^2 + 5^0 + 8^5$	$32874 := -3^1 - 2^2 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 4^3$
$32840 := 3^1 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 4^3 + 0^0$	$32859 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 9^2$	$32875 := -3^1 - 2^3 + 8^5 - 7^1 + 5^3$
$32840 := -3^2 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 4^3 + 0^0$	$32859 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 9^2$	$32876 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 7^3 - 6^3$

$32879 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 9^2$	$32899 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^1 + 9^2$	$32985 := -3^3 + 2^7 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 5^3$
$32879 := 3^3 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 9^2$	$32899 := -3^3 - 2^2 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 9^2$	$32986 := -3^1 + 2^2 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 6^3$
$32880 := -3^2 + 2^7 - 8^1 + 8^5 + 0^0$	$32908 := 3^1 + 2^7 + 9^1 + 0^1 + 8^5$	$32986 := 3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 6^1$
$32882 := -3^2 - 2^2 - 8^0 + 8^5 + 2^7$	$32928 := -3^2 + 2^5 + 9^1 + 2^7 + 8^5$	$32987 := 3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 7^1$
$32882 := 3^4 + 2^4 + 8^0 + 8^5 + 2^4$	$32928 := 3^3 + 2^2 + 9^0 + 2^7 + 8^5$	$32987 := -3^3 - 2^4 - 9^2 + 8^5 + 7^3$
$32883 := -3^1 + 2^7 - 8^0 + 8^5 - 3^2$	$32929 := -3^9 - 2^2 - 9^4 + 2^7 + 9^5$	$32988 := 3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^1 + 8^5$
$32883 := 3^4 + 2^5 + 8^0 + 8^5 + 3^0$	$32932 := -3^8 - 2^0 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 2^7$	$32988 := -3^3 + 2^8 - 9^0 + 8^5 - 8^1$
$32884 := -3^1 + 2^7 - 8^1 + 8^5 - 4^0$	$32934 := 3^8 + 2^7 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 4^0$	$32989 := 3^1 + 2^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^2$
$32885 := -3^1 - 2^2 - 8^0 + 8^5 + 5^3$	$32938 := -3^4 - 2^0 + 9^1 + 3^5 + 8^5$	$32989 := -3^3 + 2^8 + 9^0 + 8^5 - 9^1$
$32885 := 3^3 + 2^0 + 8^2 + 8^5 + 5^2$	$32944 := -3^4 + 2^8 + 9^0 + 4^7 + 4^7$	$33008 := -3^1 + 3^5 - 0^0 + 0^0 + 8^5$
$32886 := -3^1 + 2^7 - 8^0 + 8^5 - 6^1$	$32947 := -3^3 + 2^9 - 9^3 + 4^7 + 7^5$	$33028 := 3^1 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 2^8 + 8^5$
$32887 := -3^1 + 2^7 + 8^0 + 8^5 - 7^1$	$32948 := -3^1 + 2^3 - 9^2 + 4^4 + 8^5$	$33028 := -3^2 - 3^5 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 8^5$
$32888 := -3^2 + 2^0 + 8^2 + 8^2 + 8^5$	$32948 := 3^1 + 2^5 + 9^2 + 4^3 + 8^5$	$33048 := -3^1 + 3^3 + 0^1 + 4^4 + 8^5$
$32889 := -3^2 + 2^7 + 8^0 + 8^5 + 9^0$	$32949 := 3^9 + 2^7 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$33058 := -3^7 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 5^6 - 8^2$
$32890 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 0^1$	$32949 := -3^9 + 2^7 - 9^4 + 4^2 + 9^5$	$33068 := 3^1 + 3^4 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 8^5$
$32891 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 1^0$	$32968 := -3^1 - 2^2 - 9^1 + 6^3 + 8^5$	$33083 := -3^2 + 3^4 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 3^5$
$32892 := 3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 2^5$	$32968 := 3^3 + 2^7 + 9^1 + 6^2 + 8^5$	$33084 := 3^2 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 4^3$
$32892 := -3^1 - 2^1 + 8^5 + 9^0 + 2^7$	$32969 := 3^9 + 2^7 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 9^4$	$33087 := -3^3 + 3^1 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^3$
$32893 := 3^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^1 + 3^4$	$32969 := -3^9 + 2^7 - 9^4 + 6^2 + 9^5$	$33087 := 3^3 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^2$
$32893 := -3^1 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 9^0 - 3^0$	$32980 := 3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 0^1$	$33089 := -3^1 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 9^2$
$32894 := -3^1 - 2^4 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 4^3$	$32981 := 3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 1^0$	$33152 := -3^7 + 3^9 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 2^5$
$32894 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 4^1$	$32981 := -3^1 - 2^9 + 9^3 + 8^5 - 1^0$	$33156 := -3^7 + 3^9 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$32895 := -3^1 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 9^0 + 5^3$	$32982 := 3^1 + 2^1 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 2^7$	$33157 := -3^1 + 3^6 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 7^5$
$32895 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 5^1$	$32982 := -3^1 + 2^3 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 2^7$	$33158 := -3^5 + 3^2 - 1^0 + 5^4 + 8^5$
$32896 := 3^1 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 6^2$	$32983 := 3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 3^1$	$33174 := -3^2 - 3^2 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 4^7$
$32896 := -3^1 - 2^2 + 8^5 - 9^2 + 6^3$	$32983 := -3^1 - 2^4 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^5$	$33208 := -3^4 + 3^2 + 2^9 + 0^1 + 8^5$
$32897 := -3^1 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 7^2$	$32984 := 3^1 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 4^1$	$33228 := -3^1 - 3^4 + 2^5 + 2^9 + 8^5$
$32897 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 7^1$	$32984 := -3^2 - 2^5 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 4^4$	$33228 := 3^4 + 3^5 + 2^3 + 2^7 + 8^5$
$32898 := 3^2 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 9^2 + 8^5$	$32985 := 3^1 + 2^3 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 5^3$	$33243 := -3^8 - 3^8 + 2^9 + 4^8 - 3^9$
		$33244 := -3^2 - 3^3 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^7$
		$33246 := -3^8 - 3^8 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 6^6$
		$33247 := -3^1 + 3^3 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 7^5$

$33247 := 3^3 + 3^3 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^5$	$33338 := 3^1 + 3^4 + 3^5 + 3^5 + 8^5$	$33467 := -3^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^5$
$33248 := -3^1 + 3^5 - 2^4 + 4^4 + 8^5$	$33338 := -3^4 + 3^1 - 3^4 + 3^6 + 8^5$	$33467 := 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^5$
$33250 := -3^7 + 3^9 + 2^7 + 5^6 + 0^0$	$33355 := -3^4 - 3^0 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 5^6$	$33468 := -3^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 6^3 + 8^5$
$33258 := -3^5 + 3^6 - 2^0 + 5^1 + 8^5$	$33357 := -3^7 + 3^5 + 3^9 + 5^6 - 7^1$	$33469 := -3^4 - 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^6 - 9^4$
$33262 := -3^8 - 3^8 - 2^4 + 6^6 - 2^8$	$33358 := -3^2 + 3^0 - 3^3 + 5^4 + 8^5$	$33478 := -3^3 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 8^5$
$33264 := -3^9 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 4^6$	$33365 := -3^7 + 3^5 + 3^9 + 6^0 + 5^6$	$33480 := -3^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 0^1$
$33265 := -3^4 + 3^7 + 2^7 + 6^6 - 5^6$	$33377 := -3^1 + 3^2 - 3^5 + 7^5 + 7^5$	$33481 := -3^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 1^0$
$33268 := -3^1 - 3^1 + 2^9 - 6^1 + 8^5$	$33378 := -3^1 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 7^3 + 8^5$	$33482 := -3^1 - 3^5 + 4^5 + 8^5 - 2^6$
$33268 := 3^2 + 3^5 + 2^5 + 6^3 + 8^5$	$33388 := -3^3 - 3^4 + 3^6 - 8^0 + 8^5$	$33483 := -3^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 8^5 + 3^6$
$33269 := -3^2 - 3^8 - 2^8 + 6^6 - 9^4$	$33398 := -3^2 - 3^2 - 3^4 + 9^3 + 8^5$	$33484 := -3^4 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 8^5 + 4^5$
$33274 := 3^4 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$33398 := 3^4 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 8^3$	$33485 := -3^1 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 8^5 - 5^1$
$33280 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 0^1$	$33407 := -3^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 0^1 + 7^5$	$33485 := 3^3 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 5^4$
$33281 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 1^0$	$33418 := -3^4 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 8^5$	$33486 := 3^1 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^3$
$33282 := -3^1 + 3^0 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 2^9$	$33424 := -3^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 4^7$	$33486 := -3^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 8^5 - 6^3$
$33283 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 3^1$	$33427 := -3^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 2^1 + 7^5$	$33487 := -3^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 8^5 + 7^0$
$33283 := 3^3 + 3^5 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^5$	$33427 := 3^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 2^7 + 7^5$	$33488 := -3^2 + 3^6 - 4^0 + 8^0 + 8^5$
$33284 := 3^1 + 3^0 + 2^8 + 8^5 + 4^4$	$33428 := 3^1 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 2^9 + 8^5$	$33489 := -3^1 - 3^0 - 4^1 + 8^5 + 9^3$
$33284 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 4^1$	$33428 := -3^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 2^2 + 8^5$	$33498 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 9^3 + 8^5$
$33285 := 3^1 + 3^0 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 5^0$	$33442 := 3^4 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 2^9$	$33508 := 3^2 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 8^5$
$33285 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 5^1$	$33442 := -3^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 2^9$	$33533 := -3^8 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 3^9 + 3^9$
$33286 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 6^1$	$33443 := -3^3 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 3^6$	$33536 := -3^1 - 3^8 + 5^1 - 3^8 + 6^6$
$33286 := 3^3 + 3^5 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 6^3$	$33445 := -3^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 4^7 - 5^2$	$33538 := -3^1 - 3^4 + 5^3 + 3^6 + 8^5$
$33287 := 3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 7^0$	$33446 := -3^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 4^9 + 6^7$	$33538 := 3^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 3^6 + 8^5$
$33287 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 7^1$	$33447 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 4^7 + 7^5$	$33539 := 3^6 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 3^9 + 9^4$
$33288 := 3^1 + 3^0 + 2^2 + 8^3 + 8^5$	$33447 := 3^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 4^7 + 7^5$	$33539 := -3^8 - 3^9 + 5^1 + 3^6 + 9^5$
$33288 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^3 + 8^3 + 8^5$	$33448 := -3^4 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 4^2 + 8^5$	$33554 := -3^1 - 3^6 - 5^6 - 5^6 + 4^8$
$33289 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 9^1$	$33462 := -3^8 - 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^6 - 2^3$	$33560 := -3^8 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 + 0^0$
$33318 := 3^8 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 8^3$	$33464 := -3^7 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^5 + 4^6$	$33573 := -3^6 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 3^9$
$33318 := -3^8 + 3^9 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 8^3$	$33465 := -3^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 6^6 - 5^6$	$33574 := -3^5 + 3^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 + 4^7$
		$33576 := -3^4 + 3^7 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 6^6$
		$33577 := -3^1 - 3^2 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 7^5$
		$33578 := 3^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 7^2 + 8^5$

$33579 := -3^7 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3$	$33736 := -3^6 - 3^6 + 7^5 + 3^9 - 6^4$	$33826 := -3^1 - 3^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 6^4$
$33580 := 3^4 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 8^5 + 0^0$	$33738 := -3^1 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 3^6 + 8^5$	$33826 := 3^4 + 3^6 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 6^3$
$33584 := 3^4 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 4^0$	$33748 := 3^5 + 3^6 + 7^1 + 4^0 + 8^5$	$33828 := 3^2 + 3^3 + 8^3 + 2^9 + 8^5$
$33594 := -3^7 + 3^9 + 5^6 + 9^3 - 4^4$	$33756 := 3^3 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$33829 := 3^4 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 9^3$
$33597 := -3^5 - 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 7^4$	$33756 := -3^5 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 5^7 - 6^6$	$33829 := -3^8 - 3^9 + 8^3 + 2^9 + 9^5$
$33598 := -3^1 + 3^6 - 5^4 + 9^3 + 8^5$	$33757 := 3^2 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$33842 := 3^2 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 2^5$
$33623 := -3^8 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 2^3 - 3^8$	$33757 := -3^2 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$33842 := -3^2 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 2^5$
$33626 := -3^8 - 3^8 - 6^2 + 2^7 + 6^6$	$33758 := -3^7 + 3^1 + 7^2 + 5^5 + 8^5$	$33843 := -3^1 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 3^3$
$33628 := -3^1 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 2^7 + 8^5$	$33759 := -3^4 - 3^9 - 7^4 - 5^5 + 9^5$	$33843 := 3^2 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 4^4 + 3^6$
$33643 := -3^5 - 3^7 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 3^9$	$33772 := 3^1 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 2^7$	$33844 := -3^1 - 3^2 + 8^5 + 4^3 + 4^5$
$33645 := -3^3 + 3^7 - 6^6 + 4^2 + 5^7$	$33772 := -3^4 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 7^5 - 2^2$	$33844 := 3^2 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 4^5$
$33647 := -3^1 + 3^5 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 7^5$	$33773 := -3^1 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 3^4$	$33845 := -3^1 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 4^5 - 5^2$
$33648 := -3^2 + 3^4 - 6^3 + 4^5 + 8^5$	$33774 := -3^1 + 3^5 + 7^3 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$33845 := 3^3 + 3^0 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 5^2$
$33648 := 3^4 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 4^3 + 8^5$	$33775 := 3^2 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 5^3$	$33846 := 3^2 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 6^2$
$33652 := -3^1 + 3^7 - 6^6 + 5^7 - 2^0$	$33775 := -3^4 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 7^5 - 5^0$	$33846 := -3^2 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 6^2$
$33654 := -3^1 + 3^7 - 6^6 + 5^7 + 4^0$	$33776 := -3^3 - 3^3 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 6^3$	$33847 := 3^1 + 3^1 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 7^2$
$33658 := -3^8 - 3^8 + 6^6 + 5^3 - 8^0$	$33777 := 3^4 + 3^4 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 7^5$	$33847 := -3^1 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 7^2$
$33665 := -3^3 + 3^7 - 6^6 + 6^2 + 5^7$	$33777 := -3^4 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 7^5$	$33848 := -3^2 + 3^0 + 8^2 + 4^5 + 8^5$
$33668 := -3^2 + 3^6 - 6^2 + 6^3 + 8^5$	$33778 := 3^4 + 3^5 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 8^5$	$33849 := -3^3 + 3^1 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 9^2$
$33669 := -3^4 - 3^8 + 6^3 + 6^6 - 9^4$	$33779 := 3^1 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 9^2$	$33862 := -3^3 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 6^4 - 2^8$
$33682 := -3^2 + 3^7 - 6^4 + 8^5 + 2^5$	$33792 := -3^7 + 3^9 + 7^5 + 9^0 - 2^9$	$33864 := 3^2 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 4^5$
$33683 := -3^1 - 3^3 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 3^6$	$33796 := -3^4 - 3^8 + 7^3 - 9^4 + 6^6$	$33864 := -3^5 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 4^2$
$33684 := -3^4 + 3^2 - 6^2 + 8^5 + 4^5$	$33798 := 3^2 + 3^5 + 7^2 + 9^3 + 8^5$	$33865 := -3^1 - 3^6 + 8^5 - 6^4 + 5^5$
$33685 := -3^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 - 5^2$	$33804 := 3^1 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 0^1 + 4^5$	$33865 := 3^3 + 3^6 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 5^3$
$33685 := 3^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 5^3$	$33822 := 3^1 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 2^9 + 2^9$	$33866 := -3^2 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 6^4 - 6^3$
$33686 := -3^2 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 8^5 - 6^4$	$33823 := 3^4 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 3^6$	$33867 := -3^1 - 3^1 + 8^5 - 6^4 + 7^4$
$33686 := 3^5 + 3^5 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 6^3$	$33824 := -3^1 + 3^1 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 4^5$	$33876 := -3^8 - 3^8 - 8^0 + 7^3 + 6^6$
$33687 := -3^3 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 7^0$	$33824 := 3^1 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 4^5$	$33882 := 3^2 + 3^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 2^9$
$33689 := -3^3 + 3^1 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 9^3$	$33825 := -3^2 - 3^7 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 5^5$	$33884 := 3^1 + 3^4 + 8^1 + 8^5 + 4^5$
		$33884 := -3^6 - 3^7 - 8^2 + 8^5 + 4^6$
		$33885 := -3^7 + 3^5 - 8^2 + 8^5 + 5^5$
		$33886 := -3^5 + 3^0 + 8^2 + 8^5 + 6^4$

$33934 := -3^3 - 3^7 + 9^2 + 3^9 + 4^7$	$34278 := -3^3 + 4^5 + 2^9 + 7^0 + 8^5$	$34475 := -3^7 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 7^5 - 5^4$
$33936 := -3^1 - 3^4 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 6^5$	$34286 := -3^4 - 4^7 - 2^0 + 8^4 + 6^6$	$34476 := -3^3 + 4^2 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 6^4$
$33954 := -3^5 + 3^7 + 9^0 + 5^6 + 4^7$	$34296 := -3^4 - 4^7 - 2^9 + 9^5 - 6^5$	$34477 := -3^4 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 7^5$
$33954 := 3^8 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 5^3 + 4^5$	$34298 := 3^6 + 4^3 + 2^3 + 9^3 + 8^5$	$34483 := 3^6 + 4^0 + 4^4 + 8^5 + 3^6$
$33955 := -3^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 5^6 - 5^4$	$34307 := -3^7 + 4^1 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 7^5$	$34483 := -3^6 + 4^0 + 4^4 + 8^5 + 3^7$
$33957 := 3^7 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 5^5 + 7^4$	$34325 := -3^6 - 4^4 + 3^9 + 2^1 + 5^6$	$34494 := -3^3 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 9^3 + 4^7$
$33958 := -3^7 + 3^5 + 9^1 + 5^5 + 8^5$	$34325 := 3^7 + 4^7 + 3^0 + 2^7 + 5^6$	$34498 := -3^3 + 4^1 + 4^5 + 9^3 + 8^5$
$33974 := 3^3 + 3^3 + 9^3 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$34327 := -3^7 + 4^2 + 3^9 + 2^3 + 7^5$	$34498 := 3^6 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 9^3 + 8^5$
$33974 := -3^3 + 3^4 + 9^3 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$34328 := -3^1 + 4^5 + 3^3 + 2^9 + 8^5$	$34523 := -3^6 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 2^3 + 3^9$
$33982 := -3^5 + 3^6 + 9^3 + 8^5 - 2^0$	$34335 := -3^5 - 4^0 - 3^6 + 3^9 + 5^6$	$34525 := 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 2^6 + 5^6$
$33984 := 3^5 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 4^0$	$34345 := -3^1 - 4^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^6$	$34526 := -3^6 + 4^6 - 5^6 + 2^7 + 6^6$
$33984 := -3^5 + 3^6 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 4^0$	$34364 := -3^1 + 4^6 - 3^0 + 6^6 - 4^7$	$34528 := 3^6 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 8^5$
$34036 := 3^8 + 4^2 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 6^5$	$34366 := 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^7 + 6^5 + 6^5$	$34537 := -3^4 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 3^7 + 7^5$
$34038 := 3^1 + 4^5 + 0^1 + 3^5 + 8^5$	$34367 := 3^8 + 4^1 + 3^9 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$34548 := -3^1 + 4^5 - 5^6 + 4^7 + 8^5$
$34065 := -3^1 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 6^6 - 5^7$	$34368 := -3^1 + 4^3 + 3^5 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$34553 := -3^6 - 4^0 - 5^2 + 5^6 + 3^9$
$34068 := 3^1 + 4^0 + 0^1 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$34375 := -3^5 - 4^0 + 3^7 + 7^5 + 5^6$	$34563 := -3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 3^8$
$34146 := 3^4 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 4^7 + 6^4$	$34382 := -3^1 + 4^5 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 2^9$	$34566 := -3^5 - 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 6^6$
$34168 := -3^2 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 6^7 - 8^6$	$34383 := -3^2 + 4^7 - 3^7 + 8^3 + 3^9$	$34567 := -3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5$
$34205 := 3^7 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 0^0 + 5^6$	$34385 := -3^2 + 4^3 + 3^7 + 8^5 - 5^4$	$34568 := 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 8^5$
$34234 := 3^6 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7$	$34386 := -3^2 - 4^7 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 6^6$	$34569 := -3^7 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 6^4 - 9^5$
$34234 := -3^6 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^7$	$34387 := 3^2 + 4^5 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 7^3$	$34583 := -3^1 + 4^4 - 5^4 + 8^5 + 3^7$
$34235 := -3^4 - 4^5 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^6$	$34388 := 3^1 + 4^5 + 3^4 + 8^3 + 8^5$	$34586 := -3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^5 - 6^4$
$34237 := -3^7 - 4^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 7^5$	$34433 := -3^1 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 3^8 + 3^9$	$34588 := -3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^3 + 8^5$
$34238 := -3^3 + 4^4 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 8^5$	$34435 := -3^7 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 3^6 + 5^5$	$34638 := 3^4 + 4^5 + 6^2 + 3^6 + 8^5$
$34238 := 3^6 + 4^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 8^5$	$34437 := 3^8 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 7^0$	$34638 := -3^7 - 4^7 + 6^6 + 3^8 - 8^1$
$34253 := -3^3 - 4^5 - 2^2 + 5^6 + 3^9$	$34439 := 3^1 + 4^6 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 9^4$	$34639 := -3^8 + 4^5 + 6^6 + 3^4 - 9^4$
$34257 := -3^7 + 4^7 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 7^5$	$34453 := 3^7 + 4^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 3^0$	$34653 := -3^3 + 4^5 - 6^6 + 5^7 + 3^7$
$34274 := 3^3 + 4^5 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$34472 := -3^6 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 2^5$	$34655 := -3^1 + 4^3 - 6^6 + 5^5 + 5^7$
$34276 := -3^5 + 4^7 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 6^4$	$34474 := 3^1 + 4^4 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$34656 := -3^1 - 4^6 - 6^5 - 5^3 + 6^6$

$34676 := -3^3 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 6^4$	$34785 := -3^1 - 4^4 + 7^4 + 8^5 - 5^3$	$34876 := -3^4 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 7^4 - 6^3$
$34677 := 3^1 + 4^5 + 6^2 + 7^5 + 7^5$	$34786 := 3^6 + 4^5 + 7^2 + 8^5 + 6^3$	$34877 := -3^2 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 7^5 - 7^4$
$34678 := -3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^1 + 8^5$	$34787 := -3^6 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$34878 := -3^3 - 4^4 - 8^1 + 7^4 + 8^5$
$34682 := -3^7 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 2^2$	$34814 := -3^1 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 4^5$	$34883 := -3^2 + 4^0 - 8^2 + 8^5 + 3^7$
$34684 := -3^7 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 8^5 + 4^6$	$34816 := -3^8 + 4^7 + 8^5 + 1^0 - 6^5$	$34887 := -3^3 - 4^4 + 8^0 + 8^5 + 7^4$
$34685 := -3^1 - 4^0 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 5^4$	$34823 := -3^1 - 4^0 + 8^5 - 2^7 + 3^7$	$34892 := 3^5 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 2^7$
$34686 := -3^9 - 4^3 + 6^5 + 8^0 + 6^6$	$34826 := 3^6 + 4^0 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 6^4$	$34894 := -3^1 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 4^5$
$34692 := -3^8 + 4^9 - 6^7 + 9^5 - 2^2$	$34832 := -3^3 - 4^3 + 8^5 + 3^7 - 2^5$	$34896 := -3^2 + 4^7 - 8^6 + 9^3 + 6^7$
$34693 := -3^1 + 4^9 - 6^7 + 9^5 - 3^8$	$34834 := 3^2 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 4^5$	$34926 := -3^3 - 4^7 + 9^5 + 2^6 - 6^5$
$34695 := -3^8 + 4^9 - 6^7 + 9^5 - 5^0$	$34834 := -3^2 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^5$	$34938 := -3^2 + 4^0 - 9^1 + 3^7 + 8^5$
$34696 := -3^6 + 4^9 + 6^6 + 9^4 - 6^7$	$34835 := -3^4 - 4^3 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 5^2$	$34943 := -3^1 + 4^7 - 9^1 + 4^7 + 3^7$
$34697 := -3^8 + 4^9 - 6^7 + 9^5 + 7^0$	$34836 := 3^3 + 4^2 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 6^4$	$34947 := 3^1 + 4^5 + 9^3 + 4^7 + 7^5$
$34698 := 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 + 9^3 + 8^5$	$34837 := -3^3 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 7^3$	$34948 := 3^9 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 8^3$
$34724 := -3^1 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 2^9 + 4^7$	$34839 := -3^7 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 3^4 + 9^2$	$34958 := 3^7 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 8^5$
$34727 := 3^4 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 2^3 + 7^5$	$34844 := 3^3 + 4^0 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 4^5$	$34963 := -3^4 + 4^5 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 3^9$
$34728 := 3^4 + 4^5 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 8^5$	$34846 := -3^5 + 4^0 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 6^4$	$34965 := -3^4 + 4^6 - 9^2 + 6^6 - 5^6$
$34728 := -3^6 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 2^5 + 8^5$	$34852 := -3^2 - 4^5 + 8^5 + 5^5 - 2^3$	$34968 := -3^4 + 4^4 + 9^3 + 6^4 + 8^5$
$34736 := -3^6 - 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^9 - 6^0$	$34853 := -3^4 - 4^2 + 8^5 - 5^1 + 3^7$	$34980 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 0^1$
$34738 := -3^6 - 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 8^0$	$34855 := -3^2 - 4^5 + 8^5 - 5^1 + 5^5$	$34981 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 1^0$
$34744 := -3^6 - 4^4 + 7^6 - 4^7 - 4^8$	$34857 := -3^4 - 4^4 + 8^5 + 5^2 + 7^4$	$34982 := -3^5 - 4^6 + 9^4 + 8^5 - 2^3$
$34746 := 3^1 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 4^7 + 6^4$	$34858 := -3^1 - 4^5 - 8^1 + 5^5 + 8^5$	$34982 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 2^1$
$34748 := -3^7 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 4^6 + 8^5$	$34859 := -3^2 - 4^5 + 8^5 + 5^5 - 9^0$	$34983 := 3^1 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^7$
$34762 := 3^5 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 6^4 + 2^5$	$34863 := -3^3 - 4^3 + 8^5 - 6^0 + 3^7$	$34983 := -3^3 + 4^3 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^7$
$34766 := 3^5 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 6^2 + 6^4$	$34865 := -3^1 - 4^5 + 8^5 - 6^0 + 5^5$	$34984 := 3^7 + 4^1 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 4^2$
$34766 := -3^9 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 6^5 + 6^6$	$34872 := -3^2 - 4^4 + 8^5 + 7^4 - 2^5$	$34985 := -3^5 + 4^3 - 9^3 + 8^5 + 5^5$
$34782 := -3^1 - 4^4 + 7^4 + 8^5 - 2^7$	$34872 := 3^6 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 2^3$	$34985 := 3^7 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 5^2$
$34783 := -3^4 + 4^5 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 3^6$	$34873 := 3^2 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 3^6$	$34986 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 6^1$
$34784 := -3^4 + 4^5 + 7^2 + 8^5 + 4^5$	$34873 := -3^4 - 4^5 - 8^3 + 7^5 + 3^9$	$34987 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 7^1$
$34784 := 3^6 + 4^4 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 4^5$	$34874 := 3^2 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 4^5$	$34988 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 8^5$
		$34989 := -3^5 - 4^6 - 9^0 + 8^5 + 9^4$
		$34989 := 3^7 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^1$
		$34993 := 3^7 + 4^0 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 3^9$

$34993 := -3^9 + 4^0 - 9^4 + 9^5 + 3^7$	$35236 := -3^2 + 5^6 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^0$	$35310 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 0^1$
$35032 := -3^5 + 5^6 - 0^0 + 3^9 - 2^5$	$35246 := -3^2 - 5^6 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^6$	$35311 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 1^0$
$35038 := 3^4 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 3^7 + 8^5$	$35247 := -3^6 - 5^6 - 2^9 - 4^8 + 7^6$	$35312 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 2^1$
$35046 := -3^4 - 5^6 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 6^6$	$35248 := -3^6 + 5^6 - 2^7 + 4^7 + 8^4$	$35313 := 3^1 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 3^9$
$35054 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 0^0 + 5^6 + 4^7$	$35248 := 3^7 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 8^5$	$35314 := -3^6 - 5^2 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 4^7$
$35073 := -3^5 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 3^9$	$35249 := -3^5 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 9^5$	$35314 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 4^1$
$35077 := 3^5 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 7^4 + 7^5$	$35253 := -3^4 + 5^2 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 3^9$	$35315 := 3^9 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 5^6$
$35080 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 0^1$	$35258 := -3^2 - 5^4 - 2^0 + 5^5 + 8^5$	$35316 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 6^1$
$35081 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 1^0$	$35266 := -3^9 + 5^1 + 2^9 + 6^5 + 6^6$	$35317 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 7^1$
$35082 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 2^0$	$35283 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 8^5 - 3^6$	$35318 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 8^1$
$35083 := 3^1 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 3^7$	$35284 := -3^4 + 5^5 - 2^9 + 8^5 - 4^2$	$35319 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 9^0$
$35083 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 3^6$	$35285 := -3^6 + 5^3 - 2^2 + 8^5 + 5^5$	$35320 := 3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^3 + 0^0$
$35084 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 4^1$	$35286 := -3^6 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 8^5 - 6^1$	$35320 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^4 - 0^0$
$35085 := 3^7 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 5^3$	$35287 := -3^1 + 5^3 - 2^2 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$35322 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^0 + 2^4$
$35086 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 6^1$	$35287 := 3^4 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$35322 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^0 + 2^2$
$35087 := -3^4 - 5^0 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$35289 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 8^5 - 9^3$	$35325 := -3^2 + 5^2 + 3^9 + 2^0 + 5^6$
$35087 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^1$	$35289 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 9^2$	$35326 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^3 + 6^0$
$35088 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 8^5$	$35294 := -3^9 + 5^2 - 2^0 + 9^5 - 4^6$	$35328 := 3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^4 + 8^0$
$35089 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 9^1$	$35300 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 0^1$	$35331 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^3 + 3^9 - 1^0$
$35137 := -3^6 - 5^4 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 7^5$	$35301 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 1^0$	$35332 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 3^9 + 2^5$
$35158 := -3^6 - 5^1 - 1^0 + 5^5 + 8^5$	$35302 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 - 2^2$	$35333 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 3^3 + 3^9$
$35178 := 3^1 + 5^1 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$35303 := -3^1 + 5^6 - 3^1 + 0^0 + 3^9$	$35334 := -3^1 - 5^0 - 3^6 + 3^9 + 4^7$
$35208 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 8^5$	$35304 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^1 - 4^0$	$35334 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 3^9 + 4^2$
$35223 := -3^4 + 5^6 - 2^3 + 2^2 + 3^9$	$35305 := -3^1 - 5^0 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 5^6$	$35335 := 3^9 + 5^2 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 5^6$
$35228 := -3^6 + 5^5 + 2^5 + 2^5 + 8^5$	$35306 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 6^0$	$35336 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 3^9 + 6^2$
$35228 := 3^7 + 5^0 + 2^4 + 2^8 + 8^5$	$35307 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 7^0$	$35337 := -3^1 + 5^6 + 3^4 + 3^9 - 7^2$
$35230 := -3^4 + 5^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 0^0$	$35308 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 8^1$	$35337 := 3^3 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 3^9 + 7^0$
$35232 := -3^4 + 5^6 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 2^2$	$35309 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 9^1$	$35338 := -3^5 + 5^4 + 3^0 + 3^7 + 8^5$
$35234 := -3^2 + 5^6 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^3$	$35309 := 3^8 + 5^6 + 3^8 + 0^0 + 9^4$	$35339 := 3^1 + 5^6 + 3^3 + 3^9 + 9^0$
		$35340 := 3^3 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 0^0$
		$35340 := -3^6 + 5^0 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 0^0$
		$35342 := -3^6 + 5^1 + 3^9 + 4^7 - 2^0$

$35342 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 2^5$	$35396 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 6^1$	$35526 := 3^9 + 5^0 + 5^6 + 2^0 + 6^3$
$35344 := -3^3 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 4^0$	$35397 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 7^1$	$35532 := -3^3 - 5^1 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 2^8$
$35346 := -3^3 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^0$	$35398 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 8^1$	$35553 := 3^5 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 5^6 + 3^9$
$35346 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 6^2$	$35398 := -3^9 + 5^3 + 3^1 + 9^5 - 8^4$	$35559 := 3^9 + 5^3 + 5^3 + 5^6 + 9^0$
$35351 := -3^4 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 5^6 - 1^0$	$35399 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 9^2$	$35562 := 3^9 + 5^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 2^7$
$35352 := 3^1 + 5^2 + 3^9 + 5^6 + 2^4$	$35423 := -3^1 - 5^4 + 4^7 - 2^4 + 3^9$	$35567 := 3^2 + 5^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^5$
$35353 := -3^4 + 5^3 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 3^9$	$35427 := -3^1 - 5^7 - 4^6 + 2^1 + 7^6$	$35572 := 3^9 + 5^0 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 2^8$
$35355 := -3^1 + 5^2 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 5^6$	$35428 := -3^6 + 5^5 + 4^4 + 2^3 + 8^5$	$35582 := 3^7 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 8^5 + 2^0$
$35357 := -3^3 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 5^6 - 7^2$	$35432 := -3^1 + 5^6 - 4^0 + 3^9 + 2^7$	$35586 := 3^7 + 5^1 + 5^4 + 8^5 + 6^0$
$35358 := 3^1 + 5^6 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 8^4$	$35434 := -3^2 - 5^4 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 4^7$	$35592 := -3^7 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 9^4 - 2^5$
$35358 := -3^2 - 5^1 + 3^9 + 5^6 + 8^2$	$35435 := 3^9 + 5^3 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 5^6$	$35596 := -3^3 - 5^2 - 5^6 + 9^5 - 6^5$
$35363 := 3^3 + 5^6 + 3^3 + 6^0 + 3^9$	$35438 := -3^1 - 5^4 + 4^7 + 3^9 - 8^0$	$35598 := 3^5 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 9^1 + 8^4$
$35363 := -3^3 + 5^6 + 3^4 + 6^0 + 3^9$	$35443 := -3^1 - 5^4 + 4^1 + 4^7 + 3^9$	$35625 := 3^9 + 5^2 + 6^2 + 2^8 + 5^6$
$35364 := -3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 6^0 + 4^3$	$35446 := -3^5 + 5^6 - 4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5$	$35628 := -3^4 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 2^5 + 8^5$
$35367 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 6^0 + 7^2$	$35447 := 3^7 + 5^1 + 4^3 + 4^7 + 7^5$	$35628 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 2^9 + 8^5$
$35374 := -3^1 - 5^0 + 3^7 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$35449 := -3^3 + 5^7 + 4^2 + 4^7 - 9^5$	$35629 := -3^1 - 5^6 - 6^5 - 2^4 + 9^5$
$35374 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 4^3$	$35450 := 3^9 + 5^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 0^0$	$35633 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^5 + 3^9$
$35376 := -3^5 - 5^6 + 3^7 + 7^4 + 6^6$	$35462 := -3^8 - 5^2 - 4^6 + 6^6 - 2^9$	$35635 := -3^9 - 5^5 + 6^0 - 3^9 + 5^7$
$35378 := 3^1 + 5^3 + 3^4 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$35467 := -3^1 - 5^6 + 4^6 + 6^6 + 7^3$	$35637 := -3^6 - 5^3 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 7^5$
$35378 := -3^2 - 5^2 + 3^5 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$35469 := -3^3 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 9^5$	$35643 := -3^1 + 5^7 - 6^6 + 4^6 + 3^4$
$35382 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 2^6$	$35475 := -3^4 + 5^5 - 4^0 + 7^5 + 5^6$	$35644 := -3^5 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 4^7 + 4^7$
$35390 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 0^1$	$35482 := -3^3 + 5^5 - 4^4 + 8^5 - 2^7$	$35648 := -3^5 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 4^1 + 8^5$
$35391 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 1^0$	$35483 := -3^3 - 5^4 + 4^6 + 8^5 - 3^6$	$35649 := -3^1 - 5^6 - 6^5 + 4^1 + 9^5$
$35392 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 2^1$	$35484 := -3^6 + 5^5 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 4^4$	$35650 := 3^9 + 5^3 + 6^3 + 5^6 + 0^0$
$35393 := 3^1 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 9^2 + 3^9$	$35485 := -3^2 + 5^4 - 4^5 + 8^5 + 5^5$	$35657 := 3^9 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 7^3$
$35394 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 4^1$	$35486 := -3^4 - 5^0 + 4^6 + 8^5 - 6^4$	$35664 := -3^3 - 5^5 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 4^3$
$35394 := -3^6 - 5^2 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 4^7$	$35487 := -3^4 - 5^4 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$35667 := -3^4 - 5^5 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 7^1$
$35395 := 3^4 + 5^1 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 5^6$	$35487 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 7^3$	$35679 := -3^8 - 5^0 - 6^0 - 7^5 + 9^5$
$35396 := -3^2 - 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^5 - 6^5$	$35488 := 3^7 + 5^1 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 8^5$	$35682 := -3^1 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^5 + 2^3$
		$35683 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^5 - 3^5$
		$35684 := -3^2 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 8^5 + 4^6$
		$35685 := -3^5 - 5^0 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 5^5$

$35686 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^5 - 6^3$	$35809 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 0^1 + 9^3$	$35853 := -3^4 + 5^4 + 8^0 + 5^6 + 3^9$
$35687 := -3^5 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 7^0$	$35812 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 - 2^0$	$35858 := -3^2 - 5^2 - 8^0 + 5^5 + 8^5$
$35688 := 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 8^3 + 8^5$	$35814 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 4^0$	$35862 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 6^2 - 2^6$
$35732 := -3^4 + 5^6 - 7^1 + 3^9 + 2^9$	$35820 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 0^1$	$35863 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 6^3 - 3^5$
$35733 := -3^1 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 3^6 + 3^9$	$35821 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 1^0$	$35864 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 4^2$
$35733 := 3^4 + 5^6 + 7^3 + 3^0 + 3^9$	$35822 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^1 - 2^6$	$35865 := -3^2 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 6^1 + 5^5$
$35735 := -3^6 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 3^9 - 5^2$	$35822 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 2^9$	$35866 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 6^0 - 6^0$
$35737 := -3^6 - 5^2 + 7^0 + 3^9 + 7^5$	$35823 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 3^2$	$35867 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 6^1 + 7^2$
$35738 := -3^4 + 5^6 - 7^0 + 3^9 + 8^3$	$35823 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 8^3 + 2^1 + 3^0$	$35868 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 8^5$
$35738 := 3^6 + 5^1 + 7^2 + 3^7 + 8^5$	$35824 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^2 - 4^3$	$35870 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 8^3 + 7^2 + 0^0$
$35739 := -3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 3^9 - 9^3$	$35825 := -3^1 - 5^0 + 8^5 - 2^6 + 5^5$	$35872 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 7^1 - 2^0$
$35754 := -3^6 - 5^1 + 7^6 - 5^6 - 4^8$	$35825 := 3^9 + 5^0 + 8^3 + 2^2 + 5^6$	$35874 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 4^0$
$35758 := -3^1 - 5^3 - 7^1 + 5^5 + 8^5$	$35826 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 6^1$	$35876 := 3^4 + 5^4 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 6^0$
$35763 := -3^6 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 6^0 + 3^9$	$35827 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 7^1$	$35879 := -3^1 + 5^7 - 8^0 + 7^5 - 9^5$
$35768 := -3^3 + 5^4 + 7^4 + 6^0 + 8^5$	$35828 := -3^1 + 5^5 - 8^2 + 2^1 + 8^5$	$35881 := -3^1 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 8^5 - 1^0$
$35773 := -3^1 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 3^7$	$35829 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 9^1$	$35882 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 8^5 - 2^4$
$35777 := -3^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 + 7^5 + 7^5$	$35829 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 8^1 + 2^9 + 9^0$	$35883 := -3^1 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 8^5 + 3^0$
$35778 := -3^2 + 5^4 - 7^1 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$35830 := 3^2 + 5^6 + 8^3 + 3^9 + 0^0$	$35884 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 8^5 - 4^0$
$35783 := -3^4 - 5^4 + 7^5 - 8^0 + 3^9$	$35837 := -3^3 - 5^4 - 8^0 + 3^9 + 7^5$	$35884 := -3^2 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 8^5 + 4^0$
$35784 := -3^2 + 5^4 + 7^4 + 8^5 - 4^0$	$35838 := -3^4 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 3^3 + 8^5$	$35885 := 3^3 + 5^6 + 8^3 + 8^4 + 5^6$
$35786 := -3^2 + 5^4 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 6^0$	$35842 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 4^2 - 2^6$	$35885 := -3^6 - 5^3 + 8^4 + 8^5 - 5^3$
$35791 := -3^9 - 5^5 + 7^6 - 9^5 - 1^0$	$35843 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 4^1 - 3^3$	$35886 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 8^5 + 6^0$
$35793 := -3^4 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 9^1 + 3^9$	$35844 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 4^2$	$35887 := -3^2 - 5^4 + 8^4 + 8^5 - 7^3$
$35798 := 3^1 + 5^4 + 7^4 + 9^0 + 8^5$	$35845 := -3^3 - 5^1 + 8^5 - 4^2 + 5^5$	$35887 := 3^4 + 5^3 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 7^4$
$35798 := -3^8 + 5^3 - 7^5 + 9^5 - 8^1$	$35845 := 3^5 + 5^6 + 8^4 + 4^4 + 5^6$	$35888 := -3^1 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 8^5 - 8^0$
$35802 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 0^1 - 2^6$	$35846 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 4^2 - 6^2$	$35889 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 8^5 - 9^1$
$35803 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 0^1 - 3^4$	$35847 := -3^4 - 5^6 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$35890 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 9^0 - 0^0$
$35806 := -3^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 0^1 - 6^1$	$35848 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 8^5$	$35892 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 9^0 + 2^0$
$35809 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 0^1 - 9^2$	$35849 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 4^3 - 9^2$	$35894 := -3^2 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 9^1 + 4^0$
		$35896 := -3^9 + 5^4 - 8^4 + 9^5 + 6^0$
		$35897 := -3^9 - 5^5 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 7^3$
		$35898 := 3^1 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 8^5$

$35898 := -3^1 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 9^1 + 8^5$	$35998 := -3^9 - 5^0 + 9^3 + 9^5 - 8^4$	$36348 := -3^1 + 6^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 8^5$
$35902 := 3^9 + 5^6 + 9^2 + 0^0 + 2^9$	$36034 := -3^3 - 6^1 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^7$	$36348 := 3^4 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 8^5$
$35930 := 3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 0^1$	$36074 := 3^9 + 6^1 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 4^7$	$36357 := -3^9 - 6^0 - 3^9 + 5^7 - 7^4$
$35931 := 3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 1^0$	$36104 := 3^9 + 6^2 + 1^0 + 0^1 + 4^7$	$36367 := -3^4 - 6^1 + 3^9 - 6^2 + 7^5$
$35932 := 3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 2^1$	$36128 := -3^8 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 2^7 - 8^4$	$36368 := 3^4 + 6^2 + 3^7 + 6^4 + 8^5$
$35933 := 3^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^8 + 3^9$	$36233 := -3^8 + 6^6 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 3^8$	$36369 := -3^4 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 6^6 - 9^5$
$35933 := -3^8 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 3^1 - 3^9$	$36234 := 3^1 + 6^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^7$	$36372 := -3^4 - 6^2 + 3^9 + 7^5 - 2^0$
$35934 := -3^2 - 5^3 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 4^7$	$36234 := -3^4 + 6^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^7$	$36374 := -3^4 - 6^2 + 3^9 + 7^5 + 4^0$
$35934 := 3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 4^1$	$36237 := -3^1 + 6^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 7^5$	$36382 := 3^1 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 2^7$
$35935 := 3^8 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 5^5$	$36238 := -3^2 + 6^4 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 8^5$	$36384 := -3^5 + 6^1 - 3^5 + 8^5 + 4^6$
$35936 := 3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 6^1$	$36239 := 3^7 + 6^5 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 9^4$	$36385 := 3^2 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 5^3$
$35937 := -3^2 - 5^4 + 9^2 + 3^9 + 7^5$	$36243 := -3^4 + 6^0 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 3^9$	$36385 := -3^5 + 6^1 + 3^6 + 8^5 + 5^5$
$35937 := 3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 7^1$	$36258 := 3^7 + 6^4 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 8^5$	$36386 := -3^4 + 6^3 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 6^4$
$35938 := 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 + 3^3 + 8^5$	$36268 := 3^7 + 6^0 + 2^4 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$36387 := -3^1 - 6^2 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 7^5$
$35938 := -3^3 + 5^5 - 9^1 + 3^4 + 8^5$	$36273 := -3^1 - 6^3 + 2^1 + 7^5 + 3^9$	$36412 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 2^7$
$35939 := 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 9^4$	$36278 := -3^8 + 6^6 - 2^6 + 7^3 - 8^4$	$36416 := -3^8 - 6^5 + 4^6 + 1^0 + 6^6$
$35939 := -3^9 + 5^5 - 9^4 + 3^2 + 9^5$	$36284 := 3^7 + 6^4 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 4^0$	$36417 := 3^9 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 7^3$
$35948 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 9^2 + 4^0 + 8^5$	$36294 := -3^3 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 9^4 - 4^7$	$36427 := 3^9 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 7^3$
$35954 := -3^8 - 5^2 + 9^5 - 5^3 - 4^7$	$36294 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 2^1 + 9^1 + 4^7$	$36435 := 3^3 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 3^9 + 5^3$
$35976 := -3^9 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 7^2 - 6^3$	$36297 := -3^4 + 6^6 - 2^5 + 9^4 - 7^5$	$36436 := -3^7 - 6^5 - 4^4 - 3^0 + 6^6$
$35978 := 3^1 + 5^5 + 9^2 + 7^0 + 8^5$	$36324 := 3^2 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 2^5 + 4^7$	$36437 := -3^2 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 3^9 + 7^3$
$35978 := -3^1 + 5^5 + 9^2 + 7^1 + 8^5$	$36342 := 3^3 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 2^5$	$36437 := 3^8 + 6^5 + 4^2 + 3^9 + 7^4$
$35979 := 3^9 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 7^2 + 9^4$	$36342 := -3^5 + 6^1 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 2^9$	$36438 := 3^5 + 6^3 + 4^5 + 3^7 + 8^5$
$35979 := -3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2 - 7^3 + 9^5$	$36343 := -3^1 + 6^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^9$	$36447 := 3^9 + 6^2 + 4^0 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$35984 := 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 4^0$	$36343 := 3^3 + 6^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^9$	$36454 := 3^9 + 6^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 4^7$
$35984 := -3^9 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 8^0 - 4^4$	$36344 := -3^1 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 4^7$	$36457 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^2$
$35994 := 3^9 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 4^3$	$36346 := 3^3 + 6^2 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 6^3$	$36458 := -3^5 - 6^3 + 4^5 + 5^5 + 8^5$
$35994 := -3^9 - 5^1 + 9^3 + 9^5 - 4^6$	$36347 := -3^3 - 6^2 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$36468 := 3^7 + 6^3 + 4^0 + 6^4 + 8^5$
$35995 := -3^5 - 5^4 - 9^4 + 9^5 - 5^6$	$36347 := 3^5 + 6^2 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$36473 := -3^3 + 6^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 3^9$
		$36473 := 3^3 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 3^9$
		$36474 := 3^2 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 4^7$
		$36475 := -3^6 - 6^4 - 4^5 + 7^6 - 5^7$

$36478 := -3^1 + 6^4 + 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$36632 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 3^1 - 2^6$	$36723 := 3^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 2^3 + 3^9$
$36478 := 3^2 + 6^4 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$36637 := 3^8 + 6^3 + 6^5 + 3^9 + 7^4$	$36723 := -3^5 - 6^2 + 7^5 + 2^9 + 3^9$
$36485 := -3^9 + 6^5 - 4^0 + 8^5 + 5^6$	$36638 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 3^2 - 8^2$	$36724 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 2^1 + 4^2$
$36492 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 2^7$	$36639 := -3^7 - 6^4 + 6^6 + 3^3 - 9^4$	$36726 := -3^2 - 6^5 - 7^4 + 2^8 + 6^6$
$36496 := -3^8 - 6^5 + 4^6 + 9^2 + 6^6$	$36652 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 5^2 - 2^4$	$36734 := 3^3 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 4^0$
$36497 := 3^9 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 7^3$	$36653 := -3^4 - 6^4 - 6^6 + 5^7 + 3^8$	$36735 := 3^5 + 6^0 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 5^0$
$36517 := 3^9 + 6^0 + 5^2 + 1^0 + 7^5$	$36654 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 5^2 - 4^3$	$36742 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 2^5$
$36522 := -3^8 + 6^6 - 5^5 + 2^6 - 2^9$	$36656 := -3^7 - 6^2 - 6^5 - 5^0 + 6^6$	$36743 := -3^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 + 4^4 + 3^9$
$36544 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 5^1 + 4^4 + 4^7$	$36656 := 3^9 + 6^4 + 6^5 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$36743 := 3^5 + 6^1 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 3^9$
$36547 := -3^8 + 6^6 - 5^5 + 4^7 - 7^5$	$36657 := 3^9 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$36746 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 7^2 + 4^1 + 6^6$
$36547 := 3^9 + 6^2 + 5^1 + 4^2 + 7^5$	$36659 := -3^6 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 5^5 - 9^5$	$36746 := 3^9 + 6^2 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 6^3$
$36548 := -3^2 - 6^5 + 5^7 - 4^5 - 8^5$	$36662 := -3^7 + 6^0 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 2^5$	$36748 := 3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 4^4 + 8^5$
$36549 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 5^6 + 4^5 + 9^0$	$36673 := -3^3 - 6^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 3^9$	$36748 := -3^4 - 6^2 + 7^0 + 4^6 + 8^5$
$36562 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 2^8$	$36675 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 7^1 - 5^2$	$36752 := 3^9 + 6^0 + 7^5 + 5^1 + 2^8$
$36564 := -3^7 - 6^5 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 4^1$	$36678 := -3^1 + 6^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$36764 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 4^3$
$36567 := -3^7 - 6^5 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^0$	$36683 := -3^2 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 8^0 - 3^7$	$36783 := -3^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 3^9$
$36567 := 3^9 + 6^2 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^5$	$36684 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 8^1 - 4^0$	$36784 := -3^4 - 6^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 4^6$
$36568 := 3^5 + 6^3 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^5$	$36686 := -3^7 - 6^1 - 6^5 - 8^0 + 6^6$	$36788 := -3^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 8^5 - 8^4$
$36569 := -3^7 - 6^5 - 5^3 + 6^6 + 9^0$	$36687 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 8^0 - 7^1$	$36789 := 3^5 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 9^2$
$36573 := 3^4 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 3^9$	$36691 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 9^0 - 1^0$	$36798 := -3^7 - 6^0 - 7^3 + 9^4 + 8^5$
$36583 := -3^1 - 6^2 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 3^6$	$36692 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 9^0 - 2^1$	$36818 := -3^2 - 6^2 + 8^4 - 1^0 + 8^5$
$36584 := -3^5 - 6^2 - 5^0 + 8^5 + 4^6$	$36693 := -3^2 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 9^1 - 3^7$	$36824 := -3^1 - 6^2 + 8^5 - 2^0 + 4^6$
$36585 := -3^6 + 6^4 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 5^5$	$36693 := 3^6 + 6^5 + 6^5 + 9^3 + 3^9$	$36828 := -3^1 - 6^0 + 8^4 - 2^5 + 8^5$
$36587 := -3^1 + 6^4 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$36695 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 5^0$	$36834 := -3^1 - 6^2 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 4^6$
$36589 := -3^3 - 6^1 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 9^3$	$36696 := -3^7 - 6^1 - 6^5 + 9^1 + 6^6$	$36835 := -3^1 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 5^5$
$36597 := 3^9 + 6^0 + 5^2 + 9^2 + 7^5$	$36703 := -3^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 3^9$	$36837 := 3^5 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 7^3$
$36605 := 3^9 + 6^0 + 6^4 + 0^1 + 5^6$	$36707 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 7^5$	$36838 := -3^5 + 6^3 + 8^4 + 3^0 + 8^5$
$36613 := -3^4 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 1^0 - 3^7$	$36708 := 3^5 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 0^1 + 8^5$	$36842 := -3^3 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 2^2$
$36628 := -3^7 - 6^5 + 6^6 - 2^0 - 8^2$	$36722 := 3^9 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 2^3 + 2^3$	$36844 := -3^1 - 6^0 + 8^5 - 4^2 + 4^6$
		$36845 := 3^9 + 6^0 + 8^3 + 4^5 + 5^6$
		$36847 := -3^2 - 6^0 + 8^5 + 4^6 - 7^1$
		$36848 := -3^2 + 6^0 - 8^1 + 4^6 + 8^5$

$36851 := -3^6 - 6^5 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 1^0$	$36965 := -3^8 - 6^1 + 9^0 + 6^6 - 5^5$	$37229 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 2^3 + 2^8 + 9^5$
$36852 := -3^4 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 5^5 - 2^8$	$36967 := -3^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 7^5$	$37236 := 3^6 + 7^5 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 6^0$
$36853 := -3^6 - 6^5 - 8^5 + 5^7 + 3^0$	$36972 := -3^9 - 6^0 + 9^5 - 7^4 + 2^3$	$37243 := 3^6 + 7^5 + 2^3 + 4^2 + 3^9$
$36854 := -3^1 - 6^1 + 8^5 - 5^0 + 4^6$	$36973 := -3^9 - 6^0 + 9^5 - 7^4 + 3^2$	$37244 := -3^3 + 7^5 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 4^7$
$36854 := 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 5^5 + 4^2$	$36976 := -3^8 - 6^0 + 9^5 - 7^5 + 6^4$	$37246 := -3^8 - 7^4 - 2^9 + 4^3 + 6^6$
$36859 := -3^2 + 6^7 - 8^6 + 5^7 - 9^5$	$36980 := 3^7 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 0^1$	$37248 := 3^2 + 7^3 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 8^5$
$36868 := -3^1 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 6^1 + 8^5$	$36981 := 3^7 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 1^0$	$37258 := 3^6 + 7^5 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 8^4$
$36874 := 3^1 + 6^1 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 4^6$	$36982 := 3^7 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 2^1$	$37263 := 3^6 + 7^5 + 2^3 + 6^2 + 3^9$
$36874 := -3^1 + 6^1 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 4^6$	$36983 := 3^1 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 3^7$	$37263 := -3^8 - 7^4 - 2^9 + 6^6 + 3^4$
$36877 := -3^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 7^4$	$36984 := 3^1 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 4^6$	$37267 := 3^9 + 7^2 + 2^9 + 6^3 + 7^5$
$36877 := 3^9 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 7^3 + 7^5$	$36985 := 3^7 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 5^1$	$37283 := -3^2 + 7^4 - 2^6 + 8^5 + 3^7$
$36880 := 3^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 0^0$	$36986 := 3^7 + 6^1 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 6^4$	$37284 := 3^5 + 7^2 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 4^6$
$36882 := 3^2 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 2^3$	$36987 := 3^7 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 7^1$	$37286 := -3^6 - 7^4 - 2^7 + 8^5 + 6^5$
$36883 := 3^2 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 3^2$	$36988 := 3^7 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^1 + 8^5$	$37287 := -3^3 + 7^4 - 2^8 + 8^5 + 7^4$
$36883 := -3^2 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 3^3$	$36989 := 3^7 + 6^4 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3$	$37288 := -3^4 - 7^1 + 2^9 + 8^4 + 8^5$
$36884 := 3^1 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 4^2$	$37002 := 3^9 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 0^1 + 2^9$	$37289 := -3^6 - 7^5 - 2^7 - 8^4 + 9^5$
$36885 := -3^1 - 6^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 5^2$	$37029 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 0^1 + 2^6 + 9^5$	$37332 := 3^4 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 3^9 + 2^5$
$36887 := -3^3 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 7^2$	$37035 := -3^4 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 5^4$	$37335 := -3^1 + 7^6 - 3^7 + 3^0 - 5^7$
$36892 := -3^7 + 6^1 + 8^5 + 9^4 - 2^8$	$37044 := -3^5 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 4^7$	$37336 := 3^4 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 3^9 + 6^2$
$36893 := -3^5 - 6^1 + 8^5 + 9^4 - 3^7$	$37045 := 3^6 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 5^5$	$37338 := -3^2 + 7^4 - 3^2 + 3^7 + 8^5$
$36894 := -3^1 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 9^4 - 4^7$	$37083 := 3^4 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 8^3 + 3^9$	$37345 := 3^6 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 5^3$
$36898 := -3^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 + 9^0 + 8^5$	$37092 := -3^9 - 7^4 - 0^0 + 9^5 + 2^7$	$37348 := -3^2 + 7^4 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 8^5$
$36898 := 3^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 + 9^0 + 8^5$	$37139 := -3^4 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 9^3$	$37352 := 3^6 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 2^7$
$36924 := -3^9 + 6^6 - 9^4 + 2^7 + 4^7$	$37177 := 3^9 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 7^3 + 7^5$	$37353 := 3^2 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 3^9$
$36927 := -3^9 - 6^1 + 9^5 - 2^5 - 7^4$	$37193 := -3^3 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 9^3 + 3^9$	$37353 := -3^7 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 3^9$
$36928 := -3^7 - 6^3 + 9^4 + 2^1 + 8^5$	$37223 := 3^6 + 7^5 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 3^9$	$37356 := -3^8 - 7^3 + 3^6 - 5^5 + 6^6$
$36937 := -3^3 - 6^0 + 9^5 - 3^9 - 7^4$	$37225 := -3^7 + 7^6 - 2^7 + 2^4 - 5^7$	$37357 := -3^2 - 7^3 + 3^9 + 5^6 + 7^4$
$36948 := -3^1 + 6^1 + 9^2 + 4^6 + 8^5$	$37226 := 3^9 + 7^5 + 2^3 + 2^9 + 6^3$	$37358 := -3^1 + 7^4 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 8^5$
$36963 := -3^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 + 6^6 - 3^7$	$37229 := 3^9 + 7^5 + 2^1 + 2^3 + 9^3$	$37358 := 3^6 + 7^1 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 8^5$
		$37359 := 3^5 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 9^0$
		$37365 := -3^7 + 7^6 + 3^3 + 6^0 - 5^7$

$37372 := 3^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 7^5 + 2^9$	$37540 := 3^9 + 7^5 + 5^2 + 4^5 + 0^0$	$37682 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 8^1 - 2^2$
$37378 := -3^3 + 7^2 + 3^7 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$37540 := -3^9 - 7^5 + 5^7 - 4^6 + 0^0$	$37683 := -3^1 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 8^1 - 3^8$
$37384 := 3^3 + 7^4 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 4^0$	$37553 := -3^7 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 5^5 + 3^9$	$37684 := -3^9 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 4^2$
$37393 := 3^7 + 7^4 + 3^8 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$37559 := -3^9 - 7^5 - 5^4 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$37685 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 8^1 - 5^0$
$37393 := -3^7 + 7^4 - 3^7 + 9^5 - 3^9$	$37568 := -3^8 - 7^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^0$	$37686 := -3^1 - 7^5 + 6^5 + 8^2 + 6^6$
$37394 := -3^4 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 9^3 + 4^4$	$37573 := -3^7 - 7^1 - 5^7 + 7^6 + 3^5$	$37687 := 3^4 + 7^4 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 7^4$
$37396 := -3^7 + 7^0 - 3^9 + 9^5 + 6^3$	$37576 := -3^8 - 7^4 - 5^3 + 7^1 + 6^6$	$37687 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 8^1 + 7^0$
$37424 := 3^2 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 2^7 + 4^7$	$37578 := 3^1 + 7^4 + 5^1 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$37690 := -3^1 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 9^4 - 0^0$
$37428 := 3^1 + 7^2 + 4^6 + 2^9 + 8^5$	$37589 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 5^4 - 8^0 + 9^5$	$37692 := -3^1 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 9^4 + 2^0$
$37432 := -3^4 + 7^5 + 4^5 + 3^9 - 2^0$	$37590 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 5^4 + 9^5 + 0^1$	$37693 := -3^9 - 7^4 - 6^0 + 9^5 + 3^6$
$37434 := -3^4 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 4^5$	$37591 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 5^4 + 9^5 + 1^0$	$37694 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 9^0 + 4^0$
$37436 := 3^6 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 6^3$	$37592 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 5^4 + 9^5 + 2^1$	$37696 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 6^6$
$37438 := 3^4 + 7^4 + 4^0 + 3^7 + 8^5$	$37593 := -3^8 + 7^0 - 5^6 + 9^5 + 3^6$	$37708 := -3^1 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 8^4$
$37442 := 3^3 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 2^7$	$37594 := -3^7 + 7^6 - 5^7 + 9^0 + 4^4$	$37714 := 3^1 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 4^6$
$37443 := 3^2 + 7^3 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 3^9$	$37595 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 5^4$	$37732 := 3^6 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 2^9$
$37449 := 3^4 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 9^2$	$37596 := -3^1 + 7^1 - 5^6 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$37732 := -3^7 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 3^8 - 2^8$
$37463 := -3^5 + 7^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 3^9$	$37597 := -3^9 + 7^1 + 5^4 + 9^5 - 7^4$	$37734 := -3^1 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 3^3 + 4^6$
$37482 := 3^5 + 7^3 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 2^5$	$37598 := -3^9 - 7^4 + 5^4 + 9^5 + 8^1$	$37738 := 3^3 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 3^0 + 8^4$
$37483 := 3^6 + 7^5 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 3^9$	$37599 := -3^8 + 7^1 - 5^6 + 9^3 + 9^5$	$37754 := -3^2 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 4^5$
$37484 := 3^7 + 7^4 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 4^3$	$37622 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 2^3 - 2^6$	$37759 := 3^9 + 7^2 + 7^4 + 5^6 + 9^0$
$37485 := -3^1 - 7^0 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 5^4$	$37625 := -3^8 - 7^4 + 6^6 - 2^6 - 5^1$	$37794 := 3^1 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 9^2 + 4^6$
$37485 := 3^7 + 7^4 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 5^3$	$37626 := -3^1 - 7^5 + 6^5 + 2^2 + 6^6$	$37794 := -3^2 - 7^3 - 7^5 + 9^5 - 4^6$
$37486 := -3^1 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 6^4$	$37628 := -3^1 - 7^4 + 6^5 - 2^9 + 8^5$	$37796 := 3^9 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 9^1 + 6^4$
$37486 := 3^5 + 7^3 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 6^2$	$37629 := -3^4 - 7^4 + 6^6 + 2^4 - 9^4$	$37826 := 3^9 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 6^4$
$37489 := -3^7 + 7^3 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 9^4$	$37645 := 3^9 + 7^5 + 6^1 + 4^5 + 5^3$	$37827 := 3^7 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 7^4$
$37503 := 3^7 + 7^1 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 3^9$	$37647 := -3^3 + 7^5 - 6^2 + 4^6 + 7^5$	$37843 := 3^5 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 3^6$
$37534 := -3^4 + 7^6 - 5^7 + 3^7 - 4^6$	$37648 := 3^6 + 7^2 + 6^1 + 4^6 + 8^5$	$37867 := 3^4 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 7^4$
$37537 := -3^6 + 7^4 - 5^4 + 3^9 + 7^5$	$37662 := -3^3 - 7^5 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 2^6$	$37868 := -3^5 - 7^2 + 8^4 + 6^4 + 8^5$
$37538 := -3^9 - 7^5 + 5^7 - 3^0 - 8^4$	$37663 := 3^3 + 7^4 + 6^5 + 6^5 + 3^9$	$37884 := -3^1 - 7^0 + 8^4 + 8^5 + 4^5$
		$37884 := 3^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 4^2$
		$37904 := -3^5 - 7^5 + 9^5 + 0^0 - 4^6$
		$37906 := -3^7 - 7^0 - 9^4 - 0^0 + 6^6$

$37916 := -3^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 + 1^0 + 6^6$	$38324 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 2^1 + 4^6$	$38459 := -3^4 - 8^5 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 9^4$
$37932 := -3^7 - 7^5 + 9^5 - 3^7 + 2^6$	$38325 := 3^5 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 2^1 + 5^5$	$38460 := -3^1 - 8^4 - 4^6 + 6^6 - 0^0$
$37935 := -3^8 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 3^6 - 5^6$	$38334 := -3^2 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 4^5$	$38462 := -3^1 - 8^4 - 4^6 + 6^6 + 2^0$
$37936 := -3^7 + 7^0 - 9^4 + 3^3 + 6^6$	$38343 := 3^4 + 8^1 + 3^7 + 4^7 + 3^9$	$38470 := 3^9 + 8^0 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 0^0$
$37939 := -3^2 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 9^3$	$38344 := -3^6 - 8^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 4^8$	$38472 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 7^4 - 2^6$
$37949 := 3^9 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 4^0 + 9^3$	$38345 := 3^2 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5$	$38473 := -3^1 + 8^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 3^9$
$37953 := 3^5 + 7^4 + 9^0 + 5^6 + 3^9$	$38345 := -3^4 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4$	$38474 := 3^5 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 7^3 + 4^6$
$37954 := -3^7 - 7^5 + 9^5 - 5^5 + 4^5$	$38346 := -3^3 + 8^5 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 6^5$	$38475 := -3^6 - 8^2 - 4^4 + 7^6 - 5^7$
$37956 := -3^4 + 7^1 + 9^4 + 5^7 - 6^6$	$38348 := 3^5 + 8^3 + 3^6 + 4^6 + 8^5$	$38476 := -3^3 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 7^3 + 6^4$
$37957 := -3^8 - 7^5 + 9^5 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$38349 := 3^3 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 4^6 + 9^3$	$38477 := 3^9 + 8^1 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 7^4$
$37972 := -3^7 + 7^5 + 9^4 + 7^5 - 2^4$	$38360 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 0^1$	$38479 := -3^8 - 8^3 - 4^8 + 7^6 - 9^4$
$37979 := -3^7 + 7^5 - 9^1 + 7^5 + 9^4$	$38361 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 1^0$	$38489 := -3^4 - 8^4 - 4^7 + 8^0 + 9^5$
$37996 := -3^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 + 9^2 + 6^6$	$38362 := -3^1 + 8^5 - 3^7 + 6^5 + 2^3$	$38492 := -3^4 - 8^4 - 4^7 + 9^5 + 2^2$
$37997 := -3^7 + 7^5 + 9^1 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$38363 := -3^1 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 6^5 - 3^7$	$38494 := -3^8 - 8^4 - 4^7 - 9^0 + 4^8$
$37997 := 3^9 + 7^2 + 9^3 + 9^3 + 7^5$	$38364 := -3^2 + 8^5 - 3^7 + 6^5 + 4^2$	$38497 := -3^8 - 8^1 - 4^7 + 9^5 + 7^4$
$38053 := -3^3 + 8^5 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 3^7$	$38365 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 5^1$	$38499 := -3^9 - 8^2 + 4^8 - 9^3 - 9^4$
$38069 := -3^9 - 8^0 + 0^1 - 6^4 + 9^5$	$38366 := -3^1 - 8^3 + 3^0 - 6^5 + 6^6$	$38524 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 2^4 - 4^4$
$38089 := -3^6 - 8^3 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 9^4$	$38367 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 7^1$	$38540 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 0^1$
$38145 := 3^7 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 4^3 + 5^5$	$38368 := -3^7 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 8^5$	$38541 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 1^0$
$38164 := 3^1 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 6^4 + 4^6$	$38369 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 9^1$	$38542 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 2^1$
$38235 := 3^3 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 3^7 + 5^5$	$38383 := 3^6 + 8^3 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 3^7$	$38543 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 3^1$
$38252 := -3^8 - 8^5 - 2^5 + 5^7 - 2^9$	$38383 := -3^6 + 8^3 - 3^6 + 8^5 + 3^8$	$38544 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 + 4^1 - 4^4$
$38257 := -3^5 - 8^3 - 2^9 - 5^7 + 7^6$	$38386 := -3^4 - 8^4 + 3^1 - 8^4 + 6^6$	$38545 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 5^5 + 4^4 + 5^5$
$38257 := 3^7 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 7^2$	$38393 := -3^5 - 8^0 - 3^6 + 9^5 - 3^9$	$38546 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 4^3 + 6^5$
$38275 := -3^1 + 8^5 - 2^4 + 7^4 + 5^5$	$38436 := -3^3 - 8^4 - 4^6 - 3^0 + 6^6$	$38547 := -3^1 + 8^5 + 5^5 + 4^4 + 7^4$
$38285 := -3^8 - 8^3 + 2^0 - 8^5 + 5^7$	$38437 := -3^8 - 8^3 + 4^8 - 3^9 - 7^3$	$38548 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 8^1$
$38293 := -3^5 + 8^5 - 2^6 + 9^4 - 3^6$	$38456 := -3^1 - 8^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^6$	$38549 := -3^4 + 8^5 - 5^4 + 4^8 - 9^5$
$38294 := -3^1 + 8^5 - 2^3 + 9^4 - 4^5$	$38456 := 3^5 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 5^5 + 6^4$	$38563 := 3^7 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 3^7$
$38324 := 3^6 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 2^1 + 4^6$	$38457 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 4^1 + 5^7 - 7^3$	$38563 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 3^8$
		$38564 := -3^8 - 8^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 4^5$
		$38565 := -3^6 + 8^5 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 5^4$
		$38566 := 3^4 + 8^5 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 6^4$

$38583 := -3^2 + 8^3 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 3^7$	$38753 := -3^9 + 8^0 - 7^1 + 5^7 - 3^9$	$38917 := -3^9 - 8^0 - 9^5 + 1^0 + 7^6$
$38586 := -3^1 - 8^4 + 5^3 - 8^4 + 6^6$	$38763 := -3^7 + 8^3 + 7^3 + 6^6 - 3^8$	$38922 := -3^9 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 2^2 - 2^9$
$38594 := -3^6 + 8^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 - 4^0$	$38764 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 6^5 + 4^3$	$38925 := -3^8 - 8^5 + 9^0 + 2^7 + 5^7$
$38596 := -3^6 + 8^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 + 6^0$	$38765 := -3^1 + 8^5 - 7^4 + 6^5 + 5^4$	$38927 := -3^9 + 8^1 - 9^5 + 2^1 + 7^6$
$38598 := -3^6 - 8^0 - 5^0 + 9^4 + 8^5$	$38768 := -3^4 - 8^4 + 7^4 + 6^5 + 8^5$	$38928 := -3^4 - 8^2 + 9^4 - 2^8 + 8^5$
$38614 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 1^0 + 4^4$	$38769 := -3^9 - 8^3 - 7^2 - 6^2 + 9^5$	$38934 := -3^9 - 8^3 + 9^5 + 3^4 - 4^0$
$38632 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^8 - 2^2$	$38783 := -3^3 - 8^3 - 7^1 + 8^5 + 3^8$	$38936 := -3^9 - 8^3 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 6^0$
$38633 := -3^1 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^8 - 3^6$	$38789 := -3^3 - 8^3 - 7^0 + 8^5 + 9^4$	$38943 := -3^3 + 8^5 - 9^2 + 4^6 + 3^7$
$38635 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^8 - 5^0$	$38795 := -3^6 - 8^0 + 7^6 + 9^0 - 5^7$	$38947 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 7^3$
$38636 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^5 + 6^5$	$38805 := -3^8 + 8^1 - 8^5 + 0^0 + 5^7$	$38956 := -3^9 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 5^4 + 6^3$
$38637 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 7^0$	$38809 := -3^2 - 8^3 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 9^4$	$38965 := -3^9 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 6^3 - 5^4$
$38639 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^1 + 9^4$	$38813 := -3^1 - 8^3 + 8^5 - 1^0 + 3^8$	$38966 := -3^1 + 8^1 + 9^2 + 6^6 - 6^5$
$38646 := -3^5 + 8^1 - 6^5 + 4^0 + 6^6$	$38829 := -3^5 - 8^0 + 8^5 - 2^8 + 9^4$	$38967 := -3^9 - 8^4 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 7^4$
$38657 := -3^6 - 8^4 + 6^6 - 5^5 - 7^2$	$38834 := 3^6 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 4^6$	$38968 := -3^4 - 8^2 + 9^4 - 6^3 + 8^5$
$38657 := 3^7 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 5^1 + 7^4$	$38834 := -3^6 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 4^6$	$38979 := -3^9 - 8^0 - 9^3 + 7^3 + 9^5$
$38662 := -3^6 - 8^0 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 2^9$	$38835 := 3^5 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 5^5$	$38982 := -3^3 - 8^2 + 9^4 + 8^5 - 2^8$
$38663 := -3^5 - 8^0 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 3^3$	$38837 := -3^4 - 8^4 + 8^5 - 3^8 + 7^5$	$38984 := -3^4 - 8^1 + 9^4 + 8^5 - 4^4$
$38664 := -3^6 + 8^3 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 4^0$	$38849 := -3^9 - 8^0 - 8^3 - 4^1 + 9^5$	$38986 := -3^5 - 8^2 + 9^4 + 8^5 - 6^2$
$38673 := -3^3 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 7^3 - 3^7$	$38852 := -3^8 - 8^1 - 8^5 + 5^7 + 2^6$	$38997 := -3^9 - 8^0 + 9^2 - 9^5 + 7^6$
$38675 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 7^3 - 5^2$	$38855 := -3^8 + 8^2 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 5^1$	$39027 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 2^2 - 7^3$
$38678 := -3^7 - 8^4 + 6^6 + 7^4 - 8^4$	$38857 := -3^1 - 8^4 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 7^4$	$39029 := -3^9 - 9^2 + 0^1 - 2^8 + 9^5$
$38692 := -3^6 + 8^5 - 6^2 + 9^4 + 2^7$	$38859 := -3^8 + 8^2 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 9^0$	$39069 := -3^9 - 9^2 + 0^1 - 6^3 + 9^5$
$38694 := -3^7 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 9^4 + 4^4$	$38868 := -3^7 - 8^0 + 8^3 + 6^5 + 8^5$	$39075 := 3^4 + 9^4 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 5^6$
$38695 := -3^1 + 8^5 - 6^1 + 9^4 - 5^4$	$38869 := -3^5 - 8^0 + 8^5 - 6^3 + 9^4$	$39082 := -3^5 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 2^2$
$38725 := -3^4 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 2^9 + 5^5$	$38876 := -3^7 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 6^5$	$39083 := -3^1 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 3^5$
$38729 := -3^6 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 2^7 + 9^4$	$38879 := -3^6 - 8^2 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 9^4$	$39084 := -3^5 + 9^4 - 0^0 + 8^5 - 4^0$
$38743 := -3^5 - 8^5 - 7^3 + 4^8 + 3^8$	$38894 := -3^5 + 8^2 + 8^5 + 9^4 - 4^4$	$39085 := -3^5 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 5^0$
$38746 := 3^5 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 4^6 + 6^4$	$38896 := -3^6 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^4 - 6^3$	$39086 := -3^3 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 6^3$
$38749 := -3^5 - 8^5 + 7^5 - 4^6 + 9^5$	$38897 := -3^4 - 8^1 + 8^5 + 9^4 - 7^3$	$39087 := -3^5 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^0$
		$39088 := -3^5 + 9^4 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 8^5$
		$39112 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 1^0 - 2^8$

$$\begin{aligned} 39123 &:= -3^5 + 9^5 - 1^0 + 2^0 - 3^9 & 39269 &:= -3^4 - 9^3 - 2^4 + 6^6 - 9^4 & 39332 &:= -3^1 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 2^5 \\ 39133 &:= -3^5 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 3^9 & 39279 &:= -3^9 - 9^2 + 2^0 - 7^1 + 9^5 & 39333 &:= -3^2 + 9^5 - 3^3 + 3^1 - 3^9 \\ 39156 &:= -3^9 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^1 - 6^3 & 39280 &:= -3^4 + 9^4 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 0^1 & 39334 &:= -3^3 - 9^0 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 4^1 \\ 39159 &:= -3^9 - 9^2 - 1^0 - 5^3 + 9^5 & 39281 &:= -3^4 + 9^4 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 1^0 & 39335 &:= -3^2 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 3^1 - 5^2 \\ 39172 &:= -3^9 - 9^5 - 1^0 + 7^6 + 2^8 & 39282 &:= -3^3 + 9^4 - 2^2 + 8^5 - 2^4 & 39336 &:= -3^1 + 9^1 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 6^2 \\ 39173 &:= -3^5 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 7^2 - 3^9 & 39283 &:= -3^1 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 8^5 - 3^3 & 39337 &:= -3^3 - 9^0 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 7^0 \\ 39174 &:= -3^9 - 9^5 + 1^0 + 7^6 + 4^4 & 39284 &:= -3^1 - 9^5 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 4^8 & 39338 &:= -3^1 + 9^1 + 3^1 + 3^8 + 8^5 \\ 39192 &:= -3^9 + 9^2 + 1^0 + 9^5 - 2^8 & 39285 &:= -3^1 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 8^5 - 5^2 & 39338 &:= 3^1 + 9^4 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 8^5 \\ 39222 &:= -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^4 + 2^7 - 2^8 & 39286 &:= -3^1 + 9^4 - 2^2 + 8^5 - 6^2 & 39339 &:= -3^2 - 9^1 - 3^2 - 3^9 + 9^5 \\ 39223 &:= -3^4 + 9^5 - 2^6 + 2^1 - 3^9 & 39287 &:= -3^1 + 9^4 - 2^5 + 8^5 - 7^1 & 39340 &:= -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 0^1 \\ 39224 &:= -3^9 - 9^4 - 2^2 - 2^6 + 4^8 & 39288 &:= -3^2 + 9^4 + 2^5 + 8^5 - 8^2 & 39341 &:= -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 1^0 \\ 39225 &:= -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^5 + 2^4 - 5^3 & 39289 &:= -3^2 + 9^0 - 2^5 + 8^5 + 9^4 & 39342 &:= -3^2 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 - 2^4 \\ 39229 &:= -3^9 - 9^0 - 2^3 - 2^7 + 9^5 & 39290 &:= -3^9 - 9^2 + 2^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 & 39343 &:= -3^3 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 4^0 - 3^9 \\ 39238 &:= -3^2 - 9^2 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 8^5 & 39292 &:= -3^9 - 9^1 - 2^0 + 9^5 - 2^6 & 39344 &:= -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 4^1 \\ 39240 &:= -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^7 + 4^0 + 0^0 & 39293 &:= -3^4 + 9^1 - 2^0 + 9^5 - 3^9 & 39345 &:= -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 5^1 \\ 39241 &:= -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^7 + 4^1 - 1^0 & 39294 &:= -3^9 - 9^1 + 2^0 + 9^5 - 4^3 & 39346 &:= -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 6^1 \\ 39242 &:= -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^6 + 4^1 - 2^6 & 39294 &:= -3^9 - 9^1 + 2^0 + 9^5 - 4^3 & 39347 &:= -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 7^1 \\ 39243 &:= -3^4 - 9^4 + 2^5 + 4^8 - 3^9 & 39302 &:= -3^4 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 0^0 + 2^4 & 39348 &:= 3^2 + 9^1 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^5 \\ 39244 &:= -3^4 + 9^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 4^7 & 39304 &:= -3^9 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 0^0 - 4^3 & 39348 &:= -3^2 + 9^4 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 8^5 \\ 39246 &:= -3^4 - 9^4 + 2^8 - 4^5 + 6^6 & 39312 &:= -3^9 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 1^0 - 2^6 & 39349 &:= -3^2 - 9^1 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 9^5 \\ 39247 &:= -3^8 - 9^4 + 2^8 - 4^8 + 7^6 & 39313 &:= -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^3 + 1^0 - 3^9 & 39352 &:= -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 5^1 - 2^4 \\ 39248 &:= -3^1 - 9^5 - 2^2 + 4^8 + 8^5 & 39315 &:= -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 1^0 - 5^2 & 39353 &:= -3^1 - 9^1 + 3^9 - 5^0 + 3^9 \\ 39249 &:= -3^9 - 9^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 9^5 & 39317 &:= -3^9 + 9^5 - 3^0 + 1^0 - 7^2 & 39354 &:= -3^2 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 5^0 - 4^1 \\ 39259 &:= -3^9 - 9^2 - 2^0 - 5^2 + 9^5 & 39318 &:= -3^1 - 9^1 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 8^5 & 39354 &:= 3^4 + 9^2 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 4^7 \\ 39262 &:= -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^6 + 6^3 - 2^8 & 39324 &:= -3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 2^0 - 4^2 & 39355 &:= -3^9 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 5^1 - 5^2 \\ 39264 &:= -3^9 - 9^4 + 2^3 - 6^2 + 4^8 & 39327 &:= -3^6 + 9^5 - 3^7 + 2^0 - 7^5 & 39356 &:= -3^2 - 9^3 - 3^8 - 5^0 + 6^6 \\ 39266 &:= -3^6 - 9^4 - 2^6 - 6^2 + 6^6 & 39328 &:= -3^1 + 9^0 + 3^8 + 2^0 + 8^5 & 39357 &:= -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 5^0 - 7^1 \\ 39267 &:= -3^9 + 9^5 - 2^7 + 6^2 - 7^1 & 39329 &:= -3^3 - 9^1 - 3^9 - 2^0 + 9^5 & 39358 &:= 3^1 + 9^0 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 8^5 \\ 39268 &:= -3^1 + 9^4 - 2^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & 39330 &:= -3^3 - 9^1 + 3^9 + 3^9 + 0^1 & 39358 &:= -3^1 + 9^4 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 8^5 \\ & & 39331 &:= -3^3 - 9^1 + 3^9 + 3^9 + 1^0 & 39359 &:= -3^1 - 9^1 - 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^5 \\ & & & & 39362 &:= -3^1 - 9^3 - 3^8 + 6^6 - 2^0 \\ & & & & 39363 &:= -3^1 - 9^0 + 3^9 + 6^0 + 3^9 \end{aligned}$$

$39364 := -3^1 - 9^3 - 3^8 + 6^6 + 4^0$	$39393 := -3^2 + 9^1 + 3^3 + 9^5 - 3^9$	$39438 := 3^3 + 9^2 + 4^0 + 3^8 + 8^5$
$39365 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 6^0 + 5^0$	$39393 := 3^2 + 9^1 + 3^9 + 9^1 + 3^9$	$39438 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 4^0 + 3^2 + 8^2$
$39366 := -3^6 - 9^0 - 3^8 + 6^0 + 6^6$	$39394 := -3^3 - 9^1 - 3^9 + 9^5 + 4^3$	$39439 := -3^9 - 9^1 + 4^0 + 3^4 + 9^5$
$39367 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 6^0 - 7^0$	$39395 := -3^3 + 9^2 - 3^9 + 9^5 - 5^2$	$39442 := 3^4 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 2^5$
$39367 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 3^0 + 6^0 + 7^0$	$39396 := -3^9 - 9^1 + 3^1 + 9^5 + 6^2$	$39442 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 4^2 + 2^6$
$39368 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 6^1 - 8^0$	$39397 := -3^2 - 9^1 - 3^9 + 9^5 + 7^2$	$39443 := -3^1 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 4^3 - 3^9$
$39369 := -3^9 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 9^5$	$39398 := -3^1 - 9^1 + 3^4 + 9^4 + 8^5$	$39443 := 3^9 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 4^3 + 3^9$
$39369 := 3^9 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 6^0 + 9^0$	$39402 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 0^1 + 2^5$	$39445 := -3^2 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 5^3$
$39370 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 0^1$	$39403 := -3^3 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 0^1 - 3^9$	$39446 := 3^4 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 6^2$
$39371 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 1^0$	$39405 := 3^9 + 9^0 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 5^6$	$39446 := -3^6 - 9^4 + 4^2 + 4^3 + 6^6$
$39372 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^0 + 2^3$	$39405 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 0^1 - 5^2$	$39447 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 4^2 + 7^2$
$39372 := 3^9 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 2^2$	$39406 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 0^1 + 6^2$	$39448 := -3^2 + 9^4 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 8^5$
$39373 := -3^1 + 9^1 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 3^9$	$39417 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 7^2$	$39449 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 9^5$
$39373 := 3^8 + 9^4 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 3^9$	$39420 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 0^1$	$39453 := 3^9 + 9^2 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 3^9$
$39374 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 4^1$	$39421 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 1^0$	$39453 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 3^4$
$39375 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 5^1$	$39422 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 2^1 + 2^7$	$39454 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 4^0 + 5^2 + 4^3$
$39375 := 3^9 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 5^0$	$39423 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 2^6 - 3^9$	$39456 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 5^3 - 6^2$
$39376 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 6^1$	$39423 := 3^9 + 9^1 + 4^2 + 2^5 + 3^9$	$39458 := 3^1 + 9^4 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 8^5$
$39377 := -3^1 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 7^1$	$39424 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 4^1 + 2^7 + 4^8$	$39462 := -3^6 - 9^4 + 4^3 + 6^6 + 2^5$
$39377 := 3^9 + 9^1 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 7^0$	$39425 := -3^5 + 9^5 - 4^7 + 2^7 - 5^5$	$39463 := -3^1 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^2 - 3^9$
$39378 := -3^1 + 9^4 + 3^1 + 7^2 + 8^5$	$39426 := -3^6 - 9^4 - 4^1 + 2^6 + 6^6$	$39464 := -3^4 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 4^7$
$39379 := -3^1 + 9^1 - 3^9 + 7^1 + 9^5$	$39427 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 7^1$	$39465 := -3^2 - 9^4 + 4^1 + 6^6 - 5^4$
$39382 := -3^3 + 9^2 + 3^8 + 8^5 - 2^0$	$39428 := 3^1 + 9^4 + 4^3 + 2^5 + 8^5$	$39466 := -3^6 - 9^4 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 6^6$
$39384 := -3^3 + 9^2 + 3^8 + 8^5 + 4^0$	$39428 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 8^1$	$39467 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 6^2 + 7^2$
$39384 := 3^3 + 9^4 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 4^0$	$39429 := -3^9 - 9^0 - 4^3 + 2^7 + 9^5$	$39468 := -3^1 - 9^5 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 8^5$
$39387 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 8^0 - 7^1$	$39430 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 4^2 + 3^4 - 0^0$	$39469 := 3^7 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 9^4$
$39391 := -3^9 - 9^0 + 3^3 + 9^5 - 1^0$	$39432 := 3^9 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 2^6$	$39469 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 9^5$
$39392 := -3^9 + 9^0 + 3^2 + 9^5 + 2^4$	$39432 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 2^6$	$39478 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 4^0 + 7^2 + 8^2$
$39392 := 3^9 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 9^1 + 2^4$	$39434 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$39482 := 3^2 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 8^5 + 2^7$
		$39483 := 3^2 + 9^2 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 3^8$
		$39484 := 3^3 + 9^4 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 4^3$
		$39484 := -3^3 - 9^5 + 4^4 + 8^5 + 4^8$

$39485 := 3^3 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 5^3$	$39577 := -3^3 + 9^2 - 5^7 + 7^6 - 7^0$	$39643 := -3^1 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 4^3 - 3^9$
$39485 := -3^5 + 9^4 + 4^5 + 8^5 - 5^4$	$39578 := -3^2 - 9^0 - 5^7 + 7^6 + 8^2$	$39644 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 4^4$
$39486 := -3^4 - 9^4 - 4^2 - 8^3 + 6^6$	$39578 := 3^5 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 8^5$	$39645 := -3^4 - 9^4 + 6^6 + 4^4 - 5^4$
$39487 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 8^1 + 7^2$	$39579 := -3^3 + 9^0 - 5^7 + 7^6 + 9^2$	$39646 := -3^3 + 9^3 - 6^5 + 4^3 + 6^6$
$39492 := -3^9 - 9^0 - 4^0 + 9^5 + 2^7$	$39593 := -3^9 + 9^1 - 5^2 + 9^5 + 3^5$	$39647 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 4^2 + 7^2$
$39497 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 4^0 + 9^5 + 7^2$	$39594 := -3^3 + 9^2 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 4^7$	$39648 := 3^3 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 8^5$
$39507 := -3^2 - 9^1 - 5^7 + 0^0 + 7^6$	$39595 := -3^9 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 9^5 - 5^4$	$39648 := -3^7 - 9^3 + 6^6 + 4^1 - 8^4$
$39514 := -3^3 + 9^5 - 5^5 + 1^0 - 4^7$	$39596 := -3^9 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 6^3$	$39649 := -3^9 - 9^1 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 9^5$
$39517 := -3^2 + 9^0 - 5^7 + 1^0 + 7^6$	$39597 := -3^2 + 9^0 - 5^7 + 9^2 + 7^6$	$39662 := -3^6 - 9^4 - 6^3 + 6^6 + 2^9$
$39520 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 2^7 + 0^0$	$39598 := 3^5 + 9^0 + 5^2 + 9^4 + 8^5$	$39663 := -3^3 + 9^2 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 3^6$
$39522 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 2^5 - 2^0$	$39603 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 6^1 + 0^1 + 3^5$	$39664 := -3^2 + 9^3 - 6^5 + 6^6 + 4^3$
$39524 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 2^5 + 4^0$	$39606 := -3^1 + 9^3 - 6^5 + 0^1 + 6^6$	$39667 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 6^3 + 7^2$
$39532 := 3^9 + 9^1 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 2^5$	$39608 := 3^5 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 0^1 + 8^5$	$39668 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 6^3 + 6^1 + 8^3$
$39532 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 3^2 + 2^5$	$39620 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 6^0 + 2^8 - 0^0$	$39669 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 6^1 + 6^3 + 9^5$
$39533 := 3^4 + 9^2 + 5^1 + 3^9 + 3^9$	$39621 := -3^6 - 9^4 + 6^6 + 2^8 - 1^0$	$39670 := -3^4 - 9^4 + 6^6 - 7^3 - 0^0$
$39533 := -3^4 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 3^5 - 3^9$	$39622 := -3^6 - 9^4 + 6^6 + 2^7 + 2^7$	$39672 := -3^4 - 9^4 + 6^6 - 7^3 + 2^0$
$39534 := -3^2 + 9^5 - 5^5 + 3^1 - 4^7$	$39623 := -3^5 - 9^4 + 6^6 - 2^8 + 3^3$	$39674 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 6^2 + 7^3 + 4^0$
$39536 := -3^5 + 9^4 - 5^6 + 3^7 + 6^6$	$39623 := 3^9 + 9^1 + 6^3 + 2^5 + 3^9$	$39682 := 3^2 + 9^4 + 6^3 + 8^5 + 2^7$
$39536 := 3^9 + 9^1 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 6^2$	$39624 := -3^6 - 9^4 + 6^6 + 2^1 + 4^4$	$39685 := -3^5 + 9^1 + 6^5 + 8^5 - 5^4$
$39538 := 3^1 + 9^2 + 5^3 + 3^8 + 8^5$	$39625 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 2^7 + 5^3$	$39687 := 3^2 + 9^4 + 6^1 + 8^5 + 7^3$
$39538 := -3^2 + 9^4 - 5^2 + 3^5 + 8^5$	$39626 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 2^3 + 6^3$	$39687 := -3^8 - 9^0 + 6^6 - 8^2 - 7^3$
$39552 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 5^3 - 2^6$	$39627 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 2^8 - 7^0$	$39689 := 3^5 + 9^2 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 9^4$
$39554 := -3^8 - 9^0 - 5^6 + 5^7 - 4^7$	$39628 := 3^4 + 9^4 + 6^3 + 2^1 + 8^5$	$39702 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 0^0 - 2^3$
$39556 := -3^8 + 9^2 - 5^4 + 5^1 + 6^6$	$39628 := -3^7 - 9^3 + 6^6 - 2^4 - 8^4$	$39705 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 0^0 - 5^1$
$39572 := -3^4 + 9^0 - 5^7 + 7^6 + 2^7$	$39629 := -3^9 + 9^0 + 6^1 + 2^8 + 9^5$	$39708 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 0^1 - 8^0$
$39573 := 3^9 + 9^2 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 3^9$	$39632 := 3^9 + 9^1 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 2^8$	$39709 := -3^9 - 9^0 + 7^3 + 0^0 + 9^5$
$39573 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 3^4$	$39632 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 3^2 + 2^8$	$39710 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 0^1$
$39574 := -3^3 + 9^2 - 5^7 + 7^6 - 4^1$	$39635 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 3^5 + 5^2$	$39711 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 1^0$
$39576 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 7^2 + 6^2$	$39642 := -3^7 - 9^3 + 6^6 - 4^6 - 2^1$	$39712 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 2^1$
		$39713 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 3^1$
		$39714 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 4^1$
		$39715 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 5^1$

$39716 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 6^1$	$39774 := -3^3 + 9^4 + 7^2 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$39848 := 3^1 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 4^1 + 8^5$
$39717 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 7^3$	$39778 := -3^8 + 9^5 - 7^5 + 7^0 + 8^4$	$39848 := -3^2 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 4^2 + 8^5$
$39718 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 8^1$	$39790 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 0^1$	$39856 := -3^5 - 9^4 - 8^0 + 5^1 + 6^6$
$39719 := -3^9 + 9^1 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 9^5$	$39791 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 1^0$	$39860 := -3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 0^1$
$39724 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 2^4 - 4^0$	$39792 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 2^1$	$39861 := -3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 1^0$
$39726 := -3^3 - 9^4 - 7^3 + 2^0 + 6^6$	$39793 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 3^1$	$39862 := -3^4 - 9^3 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 2^7$
$39732 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 3^3 - 2^2$	$39794 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 4^1$	$39863 := -3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 3^1$
$39733 := -3^1 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 3^3 - 3^9$	$39795 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 5^1$	$39864 := 3^5 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 4^4$
$39734 := -3^2 - 9^1 + 7^5 + 3^8 + 4^7$	$39796 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 6^1$	$39864 := -3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 4^1$
$39734 := 3^9 + 9^1 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 4^2$	$39797 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 7^3$	$39865 := -3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 5^1$
$39735 := 3^9 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 5^2$	$39798 := -3^9 - 9^2 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 8^3$	$39866 := -3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^1 + 6^6$
$39735 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 3^5 + 5^3$	$39799 := -3^9 + 9^1 + 7^3 + 9^2 + 9^5$	$39867 := -3^5 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 7^1$
$39736 := -3^6 - 9^4 + 7^3 + 3^3 + 6^6$	$39804 := -3^9 - 9^4 + 8^3 + 0^1 + 4^8$	$39868 := -3^2 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 6^2 + 8^5$
$39737 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 3^3 + 7^3$	$39806 := -3^2 - 9^3 + 8^5 + 0^1 + 6^5$	$39869 := -3^2 - 9^3 + 8^3 + 6^6 - 9^4$
$39739 := -3^9 + 9^2 + 7^2 + 3^5 + 9^5$	$39822 := -3^1 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^9 - 2^4$	$39869 := 3^5 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 9^4$
$39742 := -3^2 + 9^4 + 7^5 + 4^7 - 2^0$	$39823 := -3^2 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 2^9 + 3^8$	$39878 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 8^0 + 7^0 + 8^3$
$39744 := -3^2 + 9^4 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 4^7$	$39823 := 3^5 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^3 + 3^5$	$39880 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 8^0 + 8^3 + 0^0$
$39746 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 4^0 + 6^2$	$39824 := -3^4 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^9 + 4^3$	$39882 := 3^2 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 2^5$
$39748 := -3^1 + 9^4 + 7^5 + 4^7 - 8^0$	$39825 := 3^5 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 5^3$	$39882 := -3^9 + 9^5 + 8^1 + 8^3 - 2^2$
$39752 := -3^3 - 9^0 + 7^6 - 5^7 + 2^8$	$39826 := -3^2 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^9 - 6^1$	$39883 := -3^1 + 9^5 + 8^1 + 8^3 - 3^9$
$39752 := 3^9 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 2^7$	$39827 := 3^3 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 7^3$	$39884 := 3^3 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 4^2$
$39753 := -3^4 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 5^3 - 3^9$	$39829 := -3^1 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 2^9 + 9^4$	$39885 := -3^4 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 5^3$
$39754 := -3^1 + 9^4 + 7^5 + 5^1 + 4^7$	$39829 := 3^5 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 2^8 + 9^4$	$39886 := 3^2 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 6^2$
$39754 := 3^8 + 9^0 + 7^5 + 5^0 + 4^7$	$39842 := -3^1 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 2^9$	$39886 := -3^4 - 9^4 - 8^2 - 8^2 + 6^6$
$39756 := -3^8 - 9^0 - 7^3 + 5^1 + 6^6$	$39842 := 3^8 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 4^4 + 2^8$	$39887 := -3^1 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 7^2$
$39758 := 3^4 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 5^1 + 8^5$	$39844 := 3^1 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 4^7 + 4^7$	$39933 := -3^4 - 9^2 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 3^9$
$39760 := -3^8 + 9^1 - 7^3 + 6^6 - 0^0$	$39845 := -3^5 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 4^7 - 5^6$	$39936 := -3^4 - 9^2 - 9^4 + 3^1 + 6^6$
$39762 := -3^8 + 9^1 - 7^3 + 6^6 + 2^0$	$39846 := -3^8 - 9^0 + 8^1 - 4^4 + 6^6$	$39956 := -3^5 - 9^4 + 9^3 - 5^4 + 6^6$
$39772 := -3^9 + 9^5 - 7^0 + 7^3 + 2^6$	$39847 := -3^4 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 4^4 + 7^3$	$39958 := 3^1 + 9^0 + 9^4 + 5^4 + 8^5$

$39974 := -3^9 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 4^4$	$40864 := 4^3 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 4^4$	$42289 := -4^7 - 2^7 - 2^8 + 8^1 + 9^5$
$39975 := -3^7 - 9^2 + 9^5 - 7^5 + 5^0$	$40864 := -4^7 + 0^1 - 8^3 - 6^5 + 4^8$	$42293 := -4^7 - 2^0 - 2^7 + 9^5 - 3^5$
$39978 := -3^4 + 9^3 + 9^4 + 7^0 + 8^5$	$40893 := 4^7 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 9^3 + 3^9$	$42295 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 2^8 + 9^5 - 5^4$
$39986 := -3^3 - 9^2 - 9^4 - 8^0 + 6^6$	$40976 := 4^7 + 0^1 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 6^5$	$42296 := -4^6 - 2^8 + 2^0 - 9^1 + 6^6$
$39996 := -3^2 - 9^1 - 9^2 - 9^4 + 6^6$	$41258 := -4^6 - 1^0 - 2^1 + 5^7 - 8^5$	$42306 := -4^6 - 2^8 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 6^6$
$40169 := -4^8 + 0^0 - 1^0 + 6^6 + 9^5$	$41266 := -4^6 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 6^6 - 6^4$	$42315 := -4^7 + 2^8 - 3^9 + 1^0 + 5^7$
$40169 := -4^8 - 0^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 9^5$	$41369 := -4^7 - 1^0 + 3^0 - 6^4 + 9^5$	$42316 := -4^6 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 1^0 + 6^6$
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$40286 := -4^4 - 0^0 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 6^5$	$41729 := -4^4 - 1^0 - 7^5 - 2^8 + 9^5$	$42329 := -4^7 - 2^8 - 3^4 + 2^0 + 9^5$
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$40297 := -4^7 + 0^0 + 2^5 + 9^5 - 7^4$	$41934 := -4^7 - 1^0 + 9^5 - 3^6 - 4^0$	$42336 := -4^6 - 2^3 + 3^3 - 3^5 + 6^6$
$40346 := -4^1 - 0^0 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^6$	$41936 := -4^7 - 1^0 + 9^5 - 3^6 + 6^0$	$42339 := -4^7 - 2^1 - 3^4 - 3^5 + 9^5$
$40348 := -4^1 - 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 8^5$	$41968 := -4^6 + 1^0 - 9^2 + 6^6 - 8^3$	$42349 := -4^7 + 2^0 - 3^5 + 4^8 - 9^4$
$40358 := 4^5 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^5$	$41987 := 4^4 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$42356 := -4^6 - 2^7 - 3^4 + 5^1 + 6^6$
$40363 := -4^6 - 0^0 - 3^2 + 6^6 - 3^7$	$42046 := -4^6 - 2^9 - 0^0 - 4^0 + 6^6$	$42358 := -4^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^5$
$40366 := -4^5 - 0^0 - 3^8 + 6^4 + 6^6$	$42053 := -4^7 - 2^2 - 0^0 + 5^7 - 3^9$	$42359 := -4^1 - 2^7 - 3^9 + 5^5 + 9^5$
$40367 := -4^6 + 0^0 - 3^7 + 6^6 - 7^1$	$42064 := -4^6 - 2^9 + 0^1 + 6^6 + 4^2$	$42367 := -4^6 + 2^0 - 3^5 + 6^6 + 7^2$
$40368 := -4^1 - 0^0 - 3^7 + 6^6 - 8^4$	$42089 := -4^7 - 2^6 + 0^1 - 8^3 + 9^5$	$42386 := -4^6 - 2^8 + 3^4 + 8^0 + 6^6$
$40436 := -4^6 - 0^0 + 4^3 - 3^7 + 6^6$	$42097 := -4^2 - 2^7 - 0^0 + 9^5 - 7^5$	$42389 := -4^7 - 2^5 - 3^5 - 8^0 + 9^5$
$40493 := -4^7 - 0^0 + 4^2 + 9^5 - 3^7$	$42159 := -4^7 - 2^9 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 9^5$	$42390 := -4^7 - 2^5 - 3^5 + 9^5 + 0^1$
$40546 := 4^7 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 4^7 + 6^5$	$42193 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 1^0 + 9^5 - 3^6$	$42391 := -4^7 - 2^5 - 3^5 + 9^5 + 1^0$
$40586 := 4^2 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 6^5$	$42249 := -4^4 - 2^5 - 2^7 - 4^7 + 9^5$	$42392 := -4^7 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 9^5 - 2^5$
$40608 := 4^3 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 8^5$	$42263 := -4^6 - 2^5 - 2^8 + 6^6 - 3^2$	$42393 := -4^7 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 9^5 - 3^5$
$40639 := -4^7 - 0^0 - 6^4 - 3^6 + 9^5$	$42264 := -4^4 - 2^3 - 2^5 + 6^6 - 4^6$	$42394 := -4^2 - 2^8 + 3^0 + 9^5 - 4^7$
$40685 := 4^2 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 5^3$	$42265 := -4^6 - 2^6 - 2^8 + 6^6 + 5^2$	$42395 := -4^3 - 2^5 - 3^9 + 9^5 + 5^5$
$40689 := 4^3 + 0^1 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 9^4$	$42266 := -4^6 - 2^1 - 2^8 - 6^2 + 6^6$	$42396 := -4^6 - 2^1 - 3^4 - 9^2 + 6^6$
$40693 := -4^7 - 0^0 + 6^3 + 9^5 - 3^7$	$42268 := -4^1 - 2^5 - 2^8 + 6^6 - 8^4$	$42397 := -4^7 - 2^5 - 3^5 + 9^5 + 7^1$
$40733 := 4^5 + 0^1 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 3^9$	$42279 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 2^6 + 7^6 - 9^5$	$42398 := -4^7 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 9^5 - 8^3$
$40756 := -4^3 + 0^1 + 7^6 - 5^7 + 6^4$	$42286 := -4^2 - 2^1 - 2^8 - 8^4 + 6^6$	$42399 := -4^7 - 2^5 - 3^5 + 9^1 + 9^5$
		$42409 := -4^4 - 2^0 - 4^7 + 0^0 + 9^5$
		$42426 := -4^1 - 2^1 - 4^6 - 2^7 + 6^6$
		$42429 := -4^4 + 2^2 - 4^7 + 2^4 + 9^5$

$42436 := -4^6 - 2^7 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 6^6$	$42561 := -4^6 + 2^0 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 1^0$	$42608 := -4^2 + 2^6 + 6^6 + 0^1 - 8^4$
$42456 := -4^6 - 2^7 - 4^0 + 5^2 + 6^6$	$42561 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 1^0$	$42609 := -4^6 - 2^5 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 9^2$
$42462 := -4^3 - 2^1 - 4^6 + 6^6 - 2^5$	$42562 := -4^6 + 2^0 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 2^1$	$42620 := -4^6 - 2^2 + 6^6 + 2^6 + 0^1$
$42463 := -4^3 - 2^5 - 4^6 + 6^6 - 3^0$	$42562 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 2^1$	$42621 := -4^6 - 2^1 + 6^6 + 2^6 - 1^0$
$42464 := -4^2 - 2^4 - 4^3 + 6^6 - 4^6$	$42563 := -4^6 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 3^0$	$42622 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 2^6$
$42465 := -4^3 - 2^5 - 4^6 + 6^6 + 5^0$	$42564 := -4^6 + 2^0 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 4^1$	$42623 := -4^6 - 2^1 + 6^6 - 2^4 + 3^4$
$42468 := -4^3 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 6^6 - 8^4$	$42564 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 4^1$	$42624 := -4^1 + 2^2 + 6^6 + 2^6 - 4^6$
$42469 := -4^7 - 2^7 + 4^8 + 6^1 - 9^4$	$42565 := -4^6 + 2^0 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 5^1$	$42625 := -4^6 + 2^1 + 6^6 + 2^6 - 5^0$
$42486 := -4^3 - 2^1 - 4^6 - 8^1 + 6^6$	$42565 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 5^1$	$42626 := -4^6 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 2^6 + 6^6$
$42489 := -4^4 + 2^4 - 4^7 + 8^2 + 9^5$	$42566 := -4^6 + 2^0 - 5^0 + 6^1 + 6^6$	$42627 := -4^6 + 2^1 + 6^6 + 2^4 + 7^2$
$42496 := -4^3 - 2^0 - 4^6 + 9^0 + 6^6$	$42566 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^1 + 6^6$	$42628 := -4^1 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 2^6 - 8^4$
$42497 := -4^4 + 2^9 - 4^0 + 9^5 - 7^5$	$42567 := -4^6 + 2^0 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 7^1$	$42629 := -4^6 - 2^2 + 6^6 - 2^3 + 9^2$
$42506 := -4^5 - 2^0 - 5^5 + 0^1 + 6^6$	$42567 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 7^1$	$42632 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 2^6$
$42509 := -4^7 - 2^5 - 5^3 + 0^0 + 9^5$	$42568 := -4^2 - 2^0 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^4$	$42633 := -4^6 + 2^0 + 6^6 + 3^4 - 3^2$
$42516 := -4^5 + 2^3 - 5^5 + 1^0 + 6^6$	$42569 := -4^6 + 2^0 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 9^1$	$42633 := 4^7 + 2^2 + 6^0 + 3^8 + 3^9$
$42526 := -4^6 - 2^0 - 5^0 - 2^5 + 6^6$	$42569 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 9^1$	$42634 := -4^6 + 2^0 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 4^3$
$42529 := -4^5 + 2^0 - 5^6 + 2^7 + 9^5$	$42576 := -4^6 - 2^1 + 5^2 - 7^1 + 6^6$	$42635 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 6^6 + 3^4 - 5^1$
$42534 := -4^7 - 2^5 - 5^2 - 3^8 + 4^8$	$42579 := -4^4 - 2^5 + 5^4 - 7^5 + 9^5$	$42636 := -4^6 + 2^0 - 6^1 + 3^4 + 6^6$
$42536 := -4^5 + 2^1 - 5^5 + 3^3 + 6^6$	$42592 := -4^3 - 2^8 - 5^6 + 9^5 - 2^9$	$42637 := -4^6 + 2^0 + 6^6 + 3^3 + 7^2$
$42537 := -4^8 - 2^9 - 5^6 + 3^8 + 7^6$	$42593 := -4^7 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 9^5 - 3^4$	$42638 := -4^1 + 2^0 + 6^6 + 3^4 - 8^4$
$42538 := -4^7 - 2^5 + 5^7 - 3^9 + 8^3$	$42594 := -4^3 - 2^1 - 5^1 + 9^5 - 4^7$	$42639 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 9^2$
$42539 := -4^7 - 2^1 - 5^3 + 3^0 + 9^5$	$42595 := -4^7 - 2^6 - 5^0 + 9^5 - 5^1$	$42640 := -4^6 + 2^4 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 0^1$
$42546 := -4^6 - 2^3 - 5^1 - 4^0 + 6^6$	$42596 := -4^5 + 2^3 - 5^5 + 9^2 + 6^6$	$42641 := -4^6 + 2^4 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 1^0$
$42549 := -4^7 + 2^3 - 5^3 + 4^0 + 9^5$	$42597 := -4^7 + 2^3 - 5^3 + 9^5 + 7^2$	$42642 := -4^6 + 2^1 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 2^6$
$42553 := -4^4 - 2^3 - 5^6 + 5^7 - 3^9$	$42598 := 4^2 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 8^5$	$42643 := -4^6 + 2^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 3^4$
$42556 := -4^6 - 2^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 6^6$	$42598 := -4^7 - 2^1 - 5^0 + 9^5 - 8^2$	$42644 := -4^6 + 2^2 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 4^3$
$42559 := -4^7 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 5^3 + 9^5$	$42599 := -4^3 - 2^5 - 5^6 - 9^3 + 9^5$	$42645 := -4^6 - 2^2 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 5^2$
$42560 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 0^1$	$42603 := -4^6 + 2^4 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 3^3$	$42646 := -4^6 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 4^3 + 6^6$
$42561 := -4^6 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 - 1^0$	$42607 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 6^6 - 0^0 + 7^2$	$42647 := -4^6 + 2^4 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 7^1$

$42652 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 6^6 + 5^3 - 2^5$	$42696 := -4^6 + 2^7 - 6^0 + 9^1 + 6^6$	$42864 := -4^2 + 2^6 - 8^4 + 6^6 + 4^4$
$42654 := -4^6 - 2^5 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 4^0$	$42697 := -4^7 - 2^4 - 6^0 + 9^5 + 7^2$	$42865 := -4^3 - 2^8 - 8^4 + 6^6 + 5^4$
$42659 := -4^7 - 2^0 - 6^1 + 5^0 + 9^5$	$42698 := -4^6 + 2^7 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 8^0$	$42866 := 4^5 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 6^5$
$42660 := -4^6 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 0^1$	$42699 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 6^2 - 9^0 + 9^5$	$42867 := -4^1 - 2^5 - 8^4 + 6^6 + 7^3$
$42661 := -4^6 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 1^0$	$42709 := -4^7 - 2^2 + 7^2 - 0^0 + 9^5$	$42869 := -4^7 - 2^2 - 8^1 + 6^3 + 9^5$
$42662 := -4^6 + 2^1 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 2^6$	$42719 := -4^7 + 2^2 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 9^5$	$42879 := -4^7 - 2^7 - 8^0 + 7^3 + 9^5$
$42663 := -4^6 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 3^4$	$42729 := -4^7 + 2^0 - 7^0 + 2^6 + 9^5$	$42893 := -4^7 - 2^4 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 3^5$
$42664 := -4^6 + 2^2 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 4^3$	$42729 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 7^0 + 2^6 + 9^5$	$42895 := -4^2 - 2^0 - 8^3 + 9^5 - 5^6$
$42665 := -4^6 + 2^4 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 5^3$	$42739 := -4^2 + 2^9 - 7^5 + 3^0 + 9^5$	$42896 := -4^6 + 2^8 - 8^0 + 9^2 + 6^6$
$42666 := -4^6 + 2^6 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 6^6$	$42756 := -4^4 - 2^9 - 7^1 - 5^5 + 6^6$	$42903 := -4^7 - 2^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 3^5$
$42667 := -4^6 + 2^6 - 6^1 + 6^6 + 7^2$	$42759 := -4^7 - 2^5 + 7^0 + 5^3 + 9^5$	$42904 := -4^7 - 2^4 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 4^4$
$42668 := -4^6 + 2^3 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 8^2$	$42766 := -4^6 + 2^8 - 7^2 + 6^6 - 6^0$	$42912 := -4^7 - 2^3 + 9^5 - 1^0 + 2^8$
$42669 := -4^6 - 2^3 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 9^2$	$42768 := -4^6 + 2^8 - 7^2 + 6^6 + 8^0$	$42913 := -4^7 + 2^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 3^5$
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$42674 := -4^6 + 2^0 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 4^3$	$42779 := -4^7 + 2^4 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 9^5$	$42916 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 9^5 + 1^0 - 6^1$
$42679 := -4^7 + 2^0 + 6^1 + 7^1 + 9^5$	$42791 := -4^7 + 2^7 - 7^0 + 9^5 - 1^0$	$42920 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 0^1$
$42682 := -4^1 - 2^1 + 6^6 - 8^4 + 2^7$	$42792 := -4^7 - 2^1 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 2^7$	$42921 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 1^0$
$42683 := -4^2 - 2^5 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 3^7$	$42793 := -4^4 - 2^1 + 7^5 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$42922 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 2^8$
$42684 := -4^1 + 2^6 + 6^6 + 8^2 - 4^6$	$42794 := -4^7 + 2^4 + 7^2 + 9^5 + 4^3$	$42923 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 2^4 + 3^5$
$42685 := -4^6 - 2^0 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 5^3$	$42795 := -4^3 - 2^3 - 7^5 + 9^5 + 5^4$	$42924 := -4^7 + 2^0 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^4$
$42687 := -4^4 - 2^1 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 7^4$	$42796 := -4^7 + 2^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 - 6^3$	$42925 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 5^1$
$42688 := -4^3 + 2^7 + 6^6 + 8^2 - 8^4$	$42799 := -4^7 + 2^2 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 9^5$	$42926 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 6^1$
$42689 := -4^6 - 2^4 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 9^2$	$42816 := -4^6 + 2^8 - 8^0 + 1^0 + 6^6$	$42927 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 7^1$
$42690 := -4^6 + 2^7 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 0^0$	$42826 := -4^6 + 2^1 + 8^1 + 2^8 + 6^6$	$42928 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 8^1$
$42692 := -4^7 + 2^0 - 6^1 + 9^5 + 2^5$	$42836 := -4^6 + 2^5 + 8^0 + 3^5 + 6^6$	$42929 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 9^1 + 2^8 + 9^5$
$42693 := -4^7 + 2^0 + 6^2 + 9^5 - 3^2$	$42843 := -4^1 + 2^8 + 8^5 + 4^7 - 3^8$	$42930 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 0^1$
$42693 := 4^7 + 2^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 + 3^9$	$42849 := -4^3 - 2^9 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 9^4$	$42931 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 1^0$
$42694 := -4^1 + 2^5 + 6^0 + 9^5 - 4^7$	$42863 := -4^1 + 2^6 - 8^4 + 6^6 + 3^5$	$42932 := -4^7 + 2^1 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 2^8$
$42695 := -4^6 + 2^0 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 5^3$	$42863 := 4^1 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 3^7$	$42933 := -4^7 - 2^1 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 3^5$
		$42934 := -4^2 - 2^9 + 9^5 - 3^9 + 4^6$
		$42935 := -4^1 - 2^9 + 9^5 + 3^3 - 5^6$
		$42936 := -4^7 - 2^3 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 6^2$

$42937 := -4^7 - 2^3 - 9^5 + 3^6 + 7^6$	$43062 := -4^6 - 3^2 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 2^9$	$43362 := -4^5 - 3^4 - 3^7 + 6^6 - 2^1$
$42938 := -4^7 + 2^7 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 8^2$	$43068 := -4^6 - 3^1 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 8^3$	$43363 := -4^5 - 3^0 - 3^4 + 6^6 - 3^7$
$42939 := -4^7 + 2^5 - 9^0 + 3^5 + 9^5$	$43148 := 4^6 + 3^7 + 1^0 + 4^6 + 8^5$	$43363 := 4^7 + 3^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 3^9$
$42945 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	$43162 := -4^6 + 3^6 + 1^0 + 6^6 - 2^7$	$43365 := -4^1 - 3^4 - 3^4 + 6^6 - 5^5$
$42946 := -4^7 + 2^0 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^3$	$43165 := -4^6 + 3^6 + 1^0 + 6^6 - 5^3$	$43369 := -4^6 - 3^0 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 9^3$
$42953 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 3^3$	$43168 := -4^5 - 3^8 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 8^4$	$43382 := -4^2 + 3^9 + 3^9 + 8^4 - 2^6$
$42954 := -4^7 + 2^3 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 4^4$	$43226 := -4^6 + 3^6 - 2^6 + 2^0 + 6^6$	$43383 := 4^7 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 3^9$
$42956 := -4^3 - 2^9 + 9^0 - 5^5 + 6^6$	$43236 := -4^5 - 3^4 - 2^7 - 3^7 + 6^6$	$43384 := -4^1 - 3^8 - 3^9 + 8^4 + 4^8$
$42957 := -4^1 - 2^9 + 9^5 - 5^6 + 7^2$	$43237 := -4^8 - 3^7 - 2^7 - 3^8 + 7^6$	$43386 := -4^7 - 3^8 + 3^9 - 8^1 + 6^6$
$42959 := -4^4 - 2^7 - 9^2 - 5^6 + 9^5$	$43238 := -4^4 + 3^9 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 8^4$	$43388 := -4^3 + 3^3 + 3^8 + 8^4 + 8^5$
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$42970 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 0^1$	$43256 := -4^2 - 3^1 - 2^8 - 5^5 + 6^6$	$43392 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 3^6 + 9^5 - 2^0$
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$42973 := 4^7 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 3^9$	$43263 := -4^6 - 3^3 + 2^0 + 6^6 + 3^6$	$43396 := -4^7 + 3^0 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 6^0$
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$42974 := -4^7 + 2^2 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 4^4$	$43276 := -4^5 - 3^7 - 2^9 + 7^3 + 6^6$	$43428 := 4^6 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 8^5$
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$42976 := -4^5 - 2^8 + 9^0 - 7^4 + 6^6$	$43292 := -4^7 + 3^5 + 2^7 + 9^5 + 2^8$	$43434 := 4^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 3^8 + 4^7$
$42977 := -4^7 - 2^5 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 7^3$	$43293 := -4^7 + 3^3 - 2^7 + 9^5 + 3^6$	$43435 := -4^4 - 3^7 + 4^8 - 3^9 + 5^2$
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$42979 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 9^5$	$43296 := -4^6 - 3^0 + 2^3 + 9^3 + 6^6$	$43438 := 4^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 3^8 + 8^5$
$42984 := -4^7 - 2^0 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 4^4$	$43298 := -4^7 + 3^6 - 2^5 + 9^5 - 8^2$	$43438 := -4^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 3^9 - 8^1$
$42986 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 6^0$	$43307 := 4^4 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 7^5$	$43447 := -4^1 - 3^9 - 4^0 + 4^8 - 7^4$
$42993 := -4^7 + 2^2 + 9^2 + 9^5 + 3^5$	$43324 := -4^7 + 3^6 - 3^8 + 2^2 + 4^8$	$43453 := -4^1 - 3^9 + 4^8 - 5^5 + 3^6$
$42994 := -4^7 - 2^3 + 9^2 + 9^5 + 4^4$	$43326 := -4^5 - 3^7 + 3^2 - 2^7 + 6^6$	$43456 := -4^3 - 3^3 + 4^2 - 5^5 + 6^6$
$42996 := -4^7 + 2^8 + 9^2 + 9^5 - 6^1$	$43329 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 3^6 - 2^6 + 9^5$	$43459 := -4^1 - 3^9 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 9^5$
$42997 := -4^7 - 2^1 - 9^1 + 9^5 + 7^3$	$43345 := -4^1 - 3^0 - 3^8 + 4^8 - 5^6$	$43460 := -4^5 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 6^6 - 0^0$
		$43462 := -4^5 - 3^7 + 4^0 + 6^6 + 2^4$
		$43465 := -4^3 - 3^0 - 4^0 + 6^6 - 5^5$
		$43473 := 4^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 7^1 + 3^9$

$43474 := 4^6 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 4^7$	$43655 := -4^1 + 3^1 + 6^6 + 5^3 - 5^5$	$43866 := -4^6 + 3^2 + 8^0 + 6^4 + 6^6$
$43475 := -4^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 7^6 - 5^7$	$43656 := -4^3 - 3^3 + 6^3 - 5^5 + 6^6$	$43895 := -4^1 - 3^6 - 8^5 - 9^3 + 5^7$
$43478 := 4^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 7^2 + 8^5$	$43657 := -4^6 + 3^6 + 6^6 + 5^2 + 7^3$	$43896 := -4^5 - 3^8 + 8^4 + 9^3 + 6^6$
$43498 := 4^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 8^5$	$43658 := -4^4 + 3^6 + 6^6 + 5^4 - 8^4$	$43898 := -4^4 + 3^6 + 8^4 + 9^4 + 8^5$
$43506 := -4^2 - 3^2 - 5^5 + 0^1 + 6^6$	$43660 := -4^5 - 3^7 + 6^3 + 6^6 - 0^0$	$43922 := -4^7 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 2^4 + 2^9$
$43523 := 4^5 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 2^3 + 3^9$	$43662 := -4^5 - 3^7 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 2^0$	$43926 := 4^7 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 2^1 + 6^5$
$43526 := -4^1 - 3^1 - 5^5 + 2^1 + 6^6$	$43664 := -4^6 + 3^4 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 4^5$	$43926 := -4^7 - 3^1 + 9^5 - 2^5 + 6^4$
$43542 := -4^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 4^8 + 2^8$	$43672 := -4^8 - 3^6 - 6^5 + 7^6 + 2^6$	$43942 := -4^7 - 3^1 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 2^8$
$43544 := 4^4 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 4^6 + 4^7$	$43674 := 4^7 + 3^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 + 4^7$	$43943 := -4^6 + 3^7 - 9^0 + 4^8 - 3^9$
$43546 := -4^1 + 3^1 - 5^5 + 4^2 + 6^6$	$43674 := 4^7 + 3^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 + 4^7$	$43944 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 4^5$
$43547 := -4^3 - 3^2 - 5^7 + 4^6 + 7^6$	$43678 := 4^1 + 3^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$43945 := -4^7 + 3^6 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 5^4$
$43549 := -4^7 + 3^1 + 5^4 + 4^4 + 9^5$	$43678 := -4^3 - 3^0 + 6^6 - 7^4 - 8^3$	$43960 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 0^1$
$43562 := -4^1 + 3^1 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 2^5$	$43682 := 4^6 + 3^8 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 2^8$	$43961 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 1^0$
$43563 := -4^1 + 3^2 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 3^3$	$43689 := -4^5 - 3^8 - 6^5 + 8^0 + 9^5$	$43962 := -4^1 - 3^7 + 9^1 + 6^6 - 2^9$
$43564 := -4^1 - 3^3 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 4^3$	$43692 := -4^2 - 3^7 + 6^6 - 9^3 - 2^5$	$43963 := -4^7 + 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 3^0$
$43565 := -4^3 - 3^3 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^5$	$43694 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 6^1 + 9^5 + 4^5$	$43964 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 4^1$
$43566 := -4^1 + 3^1 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 6^6$	$43695 := -4^5 - 3^0 + 6^4 + 9^5 - 5^6$	$43965 := -4^5 + 3^6 + 9^3 + 6^6 - 5^5$
$43567 := -4^1 - 3^2 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 7^2$	$43726 := -4^2 - 3^0 - 7^4 - 2^9 + 6^6$	$43966 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 6^4$
$43568 := -4^5 - 3^6 + 5^7 - 6^2 - 8^5$	$43762 := -4^2 - 3^9 + 7^5 + 6^6 - 2^1$	$43967 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 7^1$
$43569 := -4^2 - 3^3 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 9^2$	$43762 := -4^2 - 3^9 + 7^5 + 6^6 - 2^1$	$43968 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 8^1$
$43582 := 4^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 2^5$	$43763 := -4^2 - 3^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^9$	$43969 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 9^1 + 6^4 + 9^5$
$43583 := -4^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^4 + 3^9$	$43765 := -4^2 + 3^5 + 7^1 + 6^6 - 5^5$	$43983 := 4^6 + 3^9 + 9^1 + 8^3 + 3^9$
$43584 := -4^4 - 3^7 - 5^5 + 8^5 + 4^7$	$43767 := -4^2 - 3^7 - 7^3 + 6^6 - 7^3$	$44085 := 4^6 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 5^5$
$43586 := 4^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 6^2$	$43768 := -4^1 - 3^9 + 7^5 + 6^6 - 8^1$	$44176 := -4^2 - 4^3 + 1^0 - 7^4 + 6^6$
$43606 := -4^5 - 3^6 - 6^4 - 0^0 + 6^6$	$43769 := -4^7 - 3^0 + 7^4 - 6^4 + 9^5$	$44236 := -4^6 + 4^0 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 6^6$
$43607 := -4^8 - 3^6 - 6^5 - 0^0 + 7^6$	$43784 := 4^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 4^6$	$44267 := -4^1 - 4^2 + 2^5 + 6^6 - 7^4$
$43635 := -4^1 + 3^3 + 6^6 + 3^4 - 5^5$	$43784 := -4^3 + 3^8 + 7^5 + 8^4 + 4^7$	$44269 := -4^8 + 4^6 + 2^2 + 6^6 + 9^5$
$43649 := -4^7 + 3^6 - 6^0 + 4^4 + 9^5$	$43789 := -4^2 - 3^9 + 7^3 + 8^4 + 9^5$	$44285 := -4^1 - 4^6 - 2^3 + 8^5 + 5^6$
$43652 := -4^1 - 3^1 + 6^6 - 5^5 + 2^7$	$43835 := -4^3 - 3^6 - 8^5 - 3^6 + 5^7$	$44288 := -4^4 + 4^7 - 2^9 + 8^5 - 8^4$
	$43836 := 4^5 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 6^5$	$44318 := -4^5 + 4^8 - 3^9 + 1^0 - 8^3$
	$43856 := 4^7 + 3^9 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 6^5$	$44328 := -4^6 + 4^7 - 3^6 + 2^0 + 8^5$
		$44355 := -4^8 + 4^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 5^7$

$$\begin{aligned} 44358 &:= -4^5 + 4^2 + 3^2 + 5^7 - 8^5 & 44625 &:= -4^2 - 4^8 - 6^7 - 2^9 + 5^8 & 44752 &:= -4^6 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 5^6 + 2^5 \\ 44364 &:= -4^5 - 4^0 - 3^5 + 6^6 - 4^5 & 44628 &:= -4^2 + 4^6 + 6^5 + 2^2 + 8^5 & 44754 &:= -4^1 - 4^6 - 7^5 + 5^3 + 4^8 \\ 44366 &:= -4^5 - 4^5 - 3^5 + 6^0 + 6^6 & 44634 &:= -4^5 - 4^0 + 6^6 + 3^3 - 4^5 & 44756 &:= -4^6 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\ 44374 &:= -4^2 - 4^6 - 3^5 - 7^5 + 4^8 & 44636 &:= -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^0 + 3^3 + 6^6 & 44757 &:= -4^6 + 4^8 - 7^0 + 5^3 - 7^5 \\ 44395 &:= -4^7 + 4^5 + 3^4 + 9^5 + 5^4 & 44637 &:= -4^6 + 4^8 + 6^0 + 3^1 - 7^5 & 44758 &:= -4^4 - 4^8 - 7^3 + 5^7 + 8^5 \\ 44397 &:= -4^2 - 4^2 + 3^7 + 9^5 - 7^5 & 44640 &:= 4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 0^1 & 44759 &:= -4^4 - 4^7 - 7^5 + 5^7 + 9^2 \\ 44398 &:= -4^5 + 4^8 - 3^9 + 9^2 - 8^3 & 44641 &:= 4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 1^0 & 44762 &:= -4^1 - 4^0 - 7^4 + 6^6 + 2^9 \\ 44425 &:= -4^6 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 2^7 + 5^6 & 44642 &:= 4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 2^1 & 44794 &:= -4^2 - 4^4 + 7^4 + 9^5 - 4^7 \\ 44436 &:= -4^2 - 4^0 - 4^2 - 3^7 + 6^6 & 44643 &:= -4^1 - 4^4 + 6^6 - 4^5 - 3^6 & 44823 &:= -4^5 + 4^8 - 8^1 + 2^1 - 3^9 \\ 44449 &:= 4^5 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 9^4 & 44643 &:= 4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 3^1 & 44825 &:= -4^1 - 4^2 - 8^5 - 2^9 + 5^7 \\ 44463 &:= -4^1 - 4^0 - 4^0 + 6^6 - 3^7 & 44644 &:= 4^1 + 4^6 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 4^7 & 44833 &:= -4^5 + 4^8 + 8^0 + 3^1 - 3^9 \\ 44465 &:= -4^6 + 4^4 + 4^5 + 6^6 + 5^4 & 44645 &:= -4^2 - 4^5 + 6^6 - 4^6 + 5^5 & 44845 &:= -4^4 - 4^4 + 8^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 \\ 44556 &:= -4^1 + 4^5 - 5^5 + 5^1 + 6^6 & 44645 &:= 4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 & 44853 &:= -4^5 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 5^2 - 3^9 \\ 44558 &:= -4^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 5^6 + 8^5 & 44646 &:= 4^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 6^5 & 44862 &:= -4^4 - 4^5 - 8^3 + 6^6 - 2^1 \\ 44574 &:= -4^3 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 7^5 + 4^8 & 44647 &:= 4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 44863 &:= -4^4 - 4^5 - 8^3 + 6^6 - 3^0 \\ 44576 &:= -4^5 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 7^1 + 6^6 & 44648 &:= 4^1 + 4^1 + 6^5 + 4^6 + 8^5 & 44864 &:= -4^4 - 4^5 + 8^3 + 6^6 - 4^5 \\ 44579 &:= -4^7 - 4^7 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^3 & 44649 &:= 4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 9^1 & 44865 &:= -4^4 - 4^5 - 8^3 + 6^6 + 5^0 \\ 44588 &:= -4^4 - 4^0 + 5^7 - 8^3 - 8^5 & 44657 &:= -4^6 + 4^8 - 6^0 + 5^2 - 7^5 & 44887 &:= -4^6 + 4^7 - 8^3 + 8^5 + 7^3 \\ 44597 &:= -4^4 - 4^7 + 5^7 - 9^2 - 7^5 & 44665 &:= -4^7 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 6^6 + 5^6 & 44932 &:= -4^7 + 4^2 + 9^5 + 3^7 + 2^6 \\ 44598 &:= -4^5 + 4^4 + 5^7 + 9^1 - 8^5 & 44677 &:= -4^7 - 4^0 + 6^6 - 7^4 + 7^5 & 44953 &:= -4^5 + 4^8 - 9^0 + 5^3 - 3^9 \\ 44604 &:= -4^1 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 0^1 - 4^5 & 44683 &:= 4^2 + 4^6 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 3^3 & 44966 &:= -4^5 + 4^3 - 9^3 + 6^6 - 6^0 \\ 44606 &:= -4^5 - 4^5 - 6^0 - 0^0 + 6^6 & 44687 &:= -4^2 - 4^3 + 6^6 + 8^3 - 7^4 & 44967 &:= -4^2 - 4^0 + 9^3 + 6^6 - 7^4 \\ 44607 &:= -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 0^1 - 7^0 & 44688 &:= -4^2 + 4^3 + 6^5 + 8^4 + 8^5 & 44968 &:= -4^5 + 4^0 - 9^3 + 6^6 + 8^2 \\ 44608 &:= -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 0^0 - 8^0 & 44690 &:= -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 0^0 & 44974 &:= -4^6 - 4^7 - 9^2 - 7^0 + 4^8 \\ 44609 &:= -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 9^0 & 44706 &:= -4^4 - 4^6 + 7^4 + 0^0 + 6^6 & 44976 &:= -4^1 - 4^1 + 9^3 - 7^4 + 6^6 \\ 44610 &:= -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 0^0 & 44714 &:= -4^6 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 1^0 + 4^8 & 44977 &:= -4^6 + 4^8 + 9^0 + 7^3 - 7^5 \\ 44622 &:= -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 - 2^1 + 2^4 & 44735 &:= 4^5 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 3^9 + 5^5 & 44986 &:= -4^7 + 4^5 + 9^5 + 8^0 + 6^4 \\ 44623 &:= -4^5 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 2^4 - 3^0 & 44736 &:= -4^1 - 4^6 - 7^1 + 3^7 + 6^6 & 45006 &:= -4^5 - 5^4 - 0^0 + 0^1 + 6^6 \\ 44624 &:= -4^2 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 2^5 - 4^5 & 44739 &:= -4^3 - 4^7 - 7^2 + 3^7 + 9^5 & 45169 &:= -4^7 + 5^6 + 1^0 + 6^6 - 9^3 \\ & & & & 45183 &:= -4^5 + 5^6 + 1^0 + 8^5 - 3^7 \\ & & & & 45228 &:= -4^4 + 5^7 - 2^0 + 2^7 - 8^5 \\ & & & & 45234 &:= -4^7 - 5^5 - 2^6 - 3^6 + 4^8 \end{aligned}$$

$45236 := -4^3 - 5^4 - 2^1 - 3^6 + 6^6$	$45365 := -4^5 + 5^0 - 3^5 + 6^6 - 5^2$	$45498 := -4^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 9^2 - 8^5$
$45238 := -4^3 + 5^7 - 2^6 + 3^2 - 8^5$	$45366 := -4^1 + 5^0 + 3^2 + 6^6 - 6^4$	$45506 := -4^5 - 5^0 - 5^3 + 0^1 + 6^6$
$45239 := -4^7 - 5^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 9^5$	$45368 := -4^1 + 5^4 + 3^7 + 6^6 - 8^4$	$45523 := -4^7 - 5^6 + 5^7 - 2^9 - 3^4$
$45246 := -4^5 + 5^3 - 2^9 + 4^0 + 6^6$	$45382 := -4^8 + 5^7 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 2^4$	$45529 := -4^5 + 5^5 - 5^6 + 2^2 + 9^5$
$45254 := -4^6 - 5^4 + 2^6 - 5^6 + 4^8$	$45383 := -4^8 + 5^7 - 3^0 + 8^5 + 3^3$	$45546 := -4^5 - 5^2 - 5^3 + 4^3 + 6^6$
$45256 := -4^5 - 5^3 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 6^6$	$45384 := -4^6 - 5^6 + 3^4 - 8^3 + 4^8$	$45548 := -4^3 - 5^0 + 5^7 + 4^4 - 8^5$
$45258 := -4^4 + 5^3 + 2^5 + 5^7 - 8^5$	$45385 := -4^8 + 5^0 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 5^7$	$45560 := -4^6 - 5^3 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 0^1$
$45259 := -4^7 - 5^6 - 2^7 + 5^7 - 9^3$	$45386 := -4^1 - 5^2 - 3^6 - 8^3 + 6^6$	$45561 := -4^6 - 5^3 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 1^0$
$45262 := -4^4 - 5^4 - 2^0 + 6^6 - 2^9$	$45388 := -4^1 + 5^7 + 3^3 + 8^1 - 8^5$	$45562 := -4^5 - 5^0 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 2^6$
$45263 := -4^5 - 5^3 - 2^0 + 6^6 - 3^5$	$45389 := -4^7 + 5^2 + 3^7 + 8^3 + 9^5$	$45563 := -4^5 - 5^2 - 5^3 + 6^6 + 3^4$
$45264 := -4^4 - 5^4 - 2^9 + 6^6 + 4^0$	$45407 := -4^7 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 0^0 + 7^2$	$45564 := -4^3 + 5^0 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 4^5$
$45276 := -4^5 - 5^1 - 2^3 - 7^3 + 6^6$	$45418 := -4^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 1^0 - 8^5$	$45565 := -4^6 + 5^1 - 5^3 + 6^6 + 5^5$
$45278 := -4^2 + 5^7 - 2^6 + 7^0 - 8^5$	$45420 := -4^7 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 2^6 - 0^0$	$45566 := -4^5 - 5^1 - 5^2 - 6^2 + 6^6$
$45279 := -4^7 + 5^5 - 2^9 + 7^0 + 9^5$	$45422 := -4^7 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 2^0 + 2^6$	$45567 := -4^6 - 5^3 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 7^1$
$45294 := -4^6 - 5^6 - 2^9 - 9^1 + 4^8$	$45433 := -4^5 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 3^6 - 3^9$	$45568 := -4^1 - 5^0 + 5^7 + 6^3 - 8^5$
$45296 := -4^1 - 5^4 - 2^1 - 9^3 + 6^6$	$45434 := -4^1 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 3^4 - 4^7$	$45569 := -4^4 - 5^3 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 9^2$
$45297 := -4^2 - 5^6 - 2^9 + 9^5 + 7^4$	$45436 := -4^1 - 5^5 + 4^6 - 3^7 + 6^6$	$45583 := 4^1 + 5^5 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 3^8$
$45298 := -4^1 + 5^7 - 2^6 + 9^1 - 8^5$	$45437 := -4^7 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 3^4 - 7^0$	$45583 := -4^2 - 5^0 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 3^5$
$45299 := -4^6 - 5^5 + 2^5 - 9^4 + 9^5$	$45438 := -4^1 + 5^7 + 4^1 + 3^4 - 8^5$	$45584 := -4^1 - 5^2 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 4^4$
$45324 := -4^2 - 5^0 - 3^9 - 2^9 + 4^8$	$45439 := -4^5 - 5^7 + 4^8 + 3^1 + 9^5$	$45586 := -4^4 - 5^3 - 5^4 - 8^2 + 6^6$
$45326 := -4^3 - 5^2 - 3^6 - 2^9 + 6^6$	$45453 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 - 3^9$	$45588 := -4^4 - 5^2 + 5^7 + 8^3 - 8^5$
$45328 := -4^1 + 5^7 - 3^3 + 2^1 - 8^5$	$45463 := -4^4 - 5^5 + 4^0 + 6^6 + 3^7$	$45589 := -4^5 + 5^5 - 5^6 + 8^2 + 9^5$
$45342 := -4^1 + 5^1 - 3^9 + 4^8 - 2^9$	$45471 := -4^6 - 5^6 + 4^8 - 7^3 - 1^0$	$45602 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 0^0 - 2^5$
$45346 := -4^1 + 5^4 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 6^6$	$45472 := -4^1 - 5^5 + 4^8 - 7^5 - 2^7$	$45603 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 0^0 - 3^3$
$45347 := -4^4 - 5^5 - 3^0 + 4^8 - 7^5$	$45473 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 7^0 - 3^9$	$45604 := -4^1 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 0^0 - 4^5$
$45348 := -4^1 + 5^7 - 3^2 + 4^1 - 8^5$	$45474 := -4^6 - 5^1 + 4^7 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$45605 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 0^0 - 5^2$
$45362 := -4^1 - 5^4 - 3^6 + 6^6 + 2^6$	$45475 := -4^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 - 7^5 - 5^5$	$45606 := -4^5 - 5^2 - 6^0 + 0^1 + 6^6$
$45363 := -4^5 + 5^0 - 3^3 + 6^6 - 3^5$	$45478 := -4^6 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 7^5 - 8^5$	$45607 := -4^5 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 0^0 + 7^0$
$45364 := -4^1 - 5^3 - 3^7 + 6^6 + 4^5$	$45493 := -4^7 + 5^4 + 4^2 + 9^5 + 3^7$	$45608 := -4^5 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 8^0$
		$45609 := -4^5 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 0^0 + 9^0$
		$45612 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 1^0 - 2^4$
		$45614 := -4^2 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 1^0 - 4^5$

$45618 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 1^0 - 8^1$	$45650 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 0^1$	$45689 := -4^5 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 9^2$
$45619 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 1^0 - 9^1$	$45651 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 1^0$	$45692 := -4^4 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 9^2 - 2^1$
$45620 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 2^3 + 0^0$	$45652 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 2^1$	$45693 := -4^2 - 5^5 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 3^7$
$45622 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 2^0 - 2^3$	$45653 := -4^3 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 5^5 + 3^7$	$45694 := -4^3 + 5^3 + 6^6 + 9^0 - 4^5$
$45623 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 2^0 - 3^2$	$45654 := -4^1 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 5^2 - 4^5$	$45695 := -4^4 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 9^3 + 5^2$
$45624 := -4^1 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 2^0 - 4^5$	$45655 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 + 5^1 - 5^4$	$45697 := -4^7 + 5^4 + 6^1 + 9^5 + 7^4$
$45625 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 2^0 - 5^1$	$45656 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^1 - 5^4 + 6^6$	$45698 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 8^2$
$45626 := -4^5 - 5^0 - 6^0 - 2^2 + 6^6$	$45657 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 7^1$	$45699 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 9^2$
$45627 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 2^0 - 7^1$	$45658 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 8^1$	$45706 := -4^5 + 5^2 + 7^2 + 0^1 + 6^6$
$45628 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 2^1 - 8^0$	$45659 := -4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 9^1$	$45726 := -4^1 + 5^6 - 7^5 + 2^8 + 6^6$
$45629 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 2^0 - 9^0$	$45662 := -4^5 - 5^0 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 2^5$	$45728 := -4^1 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 2^5 - 8^5$
$45630 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 0^1$	$45663 := -4^5 + 5^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 3^3$	$45729 := -4^3 - 5^6 + 7^4 - 2^5 + 9^5$
$45631 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 1^0$	$45664 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 4^0$	$45743 := -4^3 - 5^7 + 7^6 + 4^6 + 3^7$
$45632 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 2^1$	$45666 := -4^5 - 5^0 - 6^0 + 6^2 + 6^6$	$45744 := -4^3 - 5^6 - 7^1 - 4^6 + 4^8$
$45633 := -4^1 - 5^5 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 3^7$	$45668 := -4^2 + 5^5 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 8^4$	$45745 := -4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3 + 4^8 - 5^5$
$45634 := -4^1 + 5^1 + 6^6 + 3^0 - 4^5$	$45669 := -4^4 - 5^0 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 9^3$	$45746 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 7^2 + 4^3 + 6^6$
$45635 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 3^0 + 5^0$	$45671 := -4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^3 - 1^0$	$45748 := -4^2 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 4^3 - 8^5$
$45636 := -4^1 - 5^3 + 6^4 - 3^7 + 6^6$	$45672 := -4^1 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^3 - 2^9$	$45762 := -4^3 + 5^2 - 7^3 + 6^6 - 2^9$
$45637 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 7^1$	$45673 := -4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^3 + 3^0$	$45763 := -4^1 - 5^5 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 3^7$
$45638 := -4^2 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 3^7 - 8^2$	$45674 := -4^5 + 5^2 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 4^2$	$45764 := -4^1 - 5^4 - 7^1 + 6^6 - 4^4$
$45639 := -4^4 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 3^3 - 9^3$	$45675 := -4^4 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 7^4 - 5^5$	$45765 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 5^3$
$45640 := -4^5 + 5^1 + 6^6 + 4^1 - 0^0$	$45676 := -4^5 + 5^0 - 6^1 + 7^2 + 6^6$	$45767 := -4^4 - 5^4 - 7^0 + 6^6 - 7^1$
$45642 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 2^3$	$45677 := -4^1 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^1 - 7^3$	$45768 := -4^4 - 5^4 + 7^0 + 6^6 - 8^1$
$45643 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 3^2$	$45678 := -4^2 + 5^7 - 6^1 + 7^3 - 8^5$	$45769 := -4^4 - 5^4 - 7^1 + 6^6 + 9^0$
$45644 := -4^5 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 4^2$	$45679 := -4^4 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 7^1 - 9^3$	$45786 := -4^5 - 5^3 + 7^3 - 8^2 + 6^6$
$45646 := -4^5 - 5^0 - 6^0 + 4^2 + 6^6$	$45682 := -4^6 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 8^0 - 2^2$	$45788 := -4^7 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^1 - 8^5$
$45648 := -4^5 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 4^2 - 8^0$	$45683 := -4^6 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 8^0 - 3^1$	$45790 := -4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 - 0^0$
$45648 := -4^5 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 8^0$	$45685 := -4^6 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 5^5$	$45790 := -4^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 + 9^5 + 0^0$
$45649 := -4^5 + 5^2 + 6^6 + 4^0 - 9^1$	$45687 := -4^5 + 5^1 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 7^2$	$45792 := -4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 2^0$
		$45796 := -4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 + 9^5 - 6^0$
		$45798 := -4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 8^0$
		$45824 := -4^6 - 5^6 + 8^0 + 2^3 + 4^8$

$45830 := -4^4 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 3^6 + 0^1$	$45896 := -4^4 - 5^0 - 8^3 + 9^1 + 6^6$	$46088 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 8^1 - 8^3$
$45831 := -4^4 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 3^6 + 1^0$	$45899 := 4^1 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^4 + 9^4$	$46095 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 0^0 + 9^2 - 5^4$
$45832 := -4^3 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 3^3 + 2^9$	$45899 := -4^2 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^4 + 9^4$	$46126 := -4^2 - 6^0 - 1^0 - 2^9 + 6^6$
$45833 := -4^4 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 3^1 + 3^6$	$45906 := -4^2 - 5^1 - 9^3 + 0^1 + 6^6$	$46128 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 1^0 + 2^0 - 8^3$
$45834 := -4^4 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 3^6 + 4^1$	$45922 := -4^7 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 2^7$	$46132 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 3^1 - 2^9$
$45835 := -4^4 + 5^1 - 8^5 + 3^6 + 5^7$	$45926 := -4^1 + 5^0 - 9^3 + 2^1 + 6^6$	$46137 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 1^0 + 3^4 - 7^3$
$45835 := 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 3^8 + 5^5$	$45942 := -4^6 - 5^6 - 9^0 + 4^8 + 2^7$	$46138 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 3^2 - 8^3$
$45836 := -4^2 - 5^4 + 8^2 - 3^5 + 6^6$	$45943 := -4^2 + 5^2 + 9^2 + 4^8 - 3^9$	$46144 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 1^0 + 4^0 - 4^4$
$45837 := -4^4 - 5^7 + 8^1 + 3^8 + 7^6$	$45945 := -4^7 - 5^0 - 9^2 + 4^8 - 5^5$	$46152 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 1^0 + 5^2 - 2^9$
$45838 := -4^4 + 5^7 + 8^1 + 3^6 - 8^5$	$45946 := -4^8 + 5^8 + 9^3 + 4^3 - 6^7$	$46154 := -4^7 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 4^4$
$45839 := -4^4 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 3^2 + 9^3$	$45947 := -4^3 - 5^7 - 9^5 + 4^8 + 7^6$	$46176 := -4^4 - 6^3 - 1^0 - 7^1 + 6^6$
$45843 := -4^1 - 5^1 - 8^0 + 4^8 - 3^9$	$45948 := -4^5 - 5^7 + 9^5 + 4^8 + 8^3$	$46178 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 7^2 - 8^3$
$45852 := -4^2 - 5^0 - 8^5 + 5^7 + 2^9$	$45962 := -4^1 - 5^2 - 9^3 + 6^6 + 2^6$	$46186 := -4^4 - 6^3 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 6^6$
$45854 := -4^3 + 5^4 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 4^3$	$45963 := -4^2 + 5^2 - 9^3 + 6^6 + 3^3$	$46204 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 0^1 + 4^3$
$45858 := -4^2 + 5^1 + 8^3 + 5^7 - 8^5$	$45964 := -4^1 + 5^2 - 9^3 + 6^6 + 4^2$	$46205 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 0^1 + 5^3$
$45859 := -4^7 + 5^1 + 8^2 + 5^5 + 9^5$	$45965 := -4^3 - 5^0 - 9^0 + 6^6 - 5^4$	$46208 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 2^7 + 0^1 - 8^3$
$45862 := -4^4 - 5^2 - 8^0 + 6^6 - 2^9$	$45967 := -4^1 - 5^1 - 9^3 + 6^6 + 7^2$	$46209 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 0^1 + 9^2$
$45863 := -4^3 + 5^0 - 8^0 + 6^6 - 3^6$	$45968 := -4^3 - 5^4 + 9^1 + 6^6 - 8^1$	$46223 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 2^1 + 3^4$
$45863 := -4^3 - 5^0 + 8^0 + 6^6 - 3^6$	$45969 := -4^3 + 5^2 + 9^2 + 6^6 - 9^3$	$46224 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 2^5 + 4^3$
$45864 := -4^4 - 5^2 - 8^3 + 6^6 + 4^0$	$45982 := -4^7 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 2^7$	$46225 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 2^1 + 2^8 - 5^4$
$45867 := -4^3 - 5^5 - 8^0 + 6^6 + 7^4$	$45984 := -4^5 - 5^6 + 9^5 - 8^3 + 4^6$	$46227 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 2^2 - 7^2$
$45869 := -4^3 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 6^6 - 9^3$	$45986 := -4^1 - 5^0 - 9^3 + 8^2 + 6^6$	$46229 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 2^3 + 9^2$
$45872 := -4^1 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 7^1 + 2^9$	$45987 := -4^1 + 5^6 - 9^0 + 8^5 - 7^4$	$46232 := -4^5 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 3^6 - 2^7$
$45876 := -4^3 - 5^5 + 8^1 + 7^4 + 6^6$	$46015 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 0^0 + 1^0 - 5^4$	$46234 := -4^5 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 3^6 + 4^0$
$45879 := -4^4 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 7^2 + 9^3$	$46025 := -4^7 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 2^7 + 5^6$	$46235 := -4^5 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 3^6 - 5^3$
$45879 := 4^5 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 9^4$	$46035 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 0^0 + 3^2 - 5^4$	$46243 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 3^6$
$45886 := -4^4 - 5^0 - 8^0 - 8^3 + 6^6$	$46057 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 0^0 + 5^0 - 7^3$	$46245 := -4^5 + 6^6 - 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^4$
$45893 := -4^7 - 5^4 + 8^4 + 9^5 - 3^5$	$46075 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 0^0 + 7^2 - 5^4$	$46246 := -4^4 - 6^3 - 2^1 + 4^3 + 6^6$
$45894 := -4^4 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 9^3 + 4^3$	$46082 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 0^0 + 8^0 - 2^9$	$46247 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 7^3$
		$46249 := -4^5 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 9^3$
		$46250 := -4^5 + 6^6 - 2^3 + 5^4 + 0^0$

$$\begin{aligned} 46252 &:= -4^2 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 5^3 - 2^9 & 46288 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 8^1 + 8^1 & 46348 &:= -4^2 - 6^0 - 3^9 + 4^8 + 8^3 \\ 46253 &:= -4^5 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 5^4 - 3^1 & 46289 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 8^1 + 9^1 & 46349 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 4^0 - 9^0 \\ 46254 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 + 2^0 + 5^4 - 4^5 & 46296 &:= -4^3 - 6^3 + 2^0 - 9^2 + 6^6 & 46350 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 0^1 \\ 46255 &:= -4^5 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 5^4 - 5^0 & 46297 &:= -4^2 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 9^0 - 7^3 & 46351 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 1^0 \\ 46256 &:= -4^5 + 6^0 - 2^1 + 5^4 + 6^6 & 46298 &:= -4^5 + 6^6 + 2^0 + 9^3 - 8^2 & 46352 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^2 + 5^2 - 2^8 \\ 46257 &:= -4^5 + 6^6 + 2^0 + 5^4 - 7^0 & 46304 &:= -4^2 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 0^0 - 4^4 & 46353 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 5^2 - 3^5 \\ 46257 &:= -4^5 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 5^4 + 7^0 & 46307 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 - 3^1 + 0^0 - 7^3 & 46354 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 4^1 \\ 46258 &:= -4^5 + 6^6 + 2^1 + 5^4 - 8^0 & 46312 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 1^0 - 2^3 & 46355 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 5^1 \\ 46259 &:= -4^5 + 6^6 + 2^0 + 5^4 + 9^0 & 46315 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 1^0 - 5^1 & 46356 &:= -4^1 - 6^3 - 3^4 + 5^0 + 6^6 \\ 46262 &:= -4^1 - 6^1 - 2^7 + 6^6 - 2^8 & 46319 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 1^0 - 9^2 & 46357 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 7^1 \\ 46263 &:= -4^2 - 6^1 - 2^7 + 6^6 - 3^5 & 46320 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 2^0 + 0^1 & 46358 &:= -4^2 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^2 - 8^2 \\ 46264 &:= -4^3 - 6^3 - 2^7 + 6^6 + 4^2 & 46321 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 2^0 + 1^0 & 46359 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 9^1 \\ 46265 &:= -4^1 - 6^1 - 2^8 + 6^6 - 5^3 & 46322 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 2^0 + 2^1 & 46360 &:= -4^2 - 6^2 - 3^5 + 6^6 - 0^0 \\ 46267 &:= -4^1 - 6^3 - 2^9 + 6^6 + 7^3 & 46323 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 2^0 - 3^5 & 46361 &:= -4^5 + 6^0 + 3^6 + 6^6 - 1^0 \\ 46268 &:= -4^4 - 6^2 - 2^5 + 6^6 - 8^2 & 46324 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 2^0 + 4^1 & 46361 &:= -4^5 - 6^0 + 3^6 + 6^6 + 1^0 \\ 46269 &:= -4^4 + 6^1 - 2^7 + 6^6 - 9^1 & 46325 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 2^0 - 5^2 & 46362 &:= -4^2 - 6^2 - 3^5 + 6^6 + 2^0 \\ 46272 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 7^0 - 2^7 & 46326 &:= -4^3 - 6^0 - 3^2 - 2^8 + 6^6 & 46363 &:= -4^4 - 6^0 - 3^2 + 6^6 - 3^3 \\ 46274 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 7^0 + 4^0 & 46327 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 2^0 + 7^1 & 46364 &:= -4^3 + 6^0 + 3^3 + 6^6 - 4^4 \\ 46275 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 7^0 - 5^3 & 46328 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^2 + 2^0 - 8^2 & 46365 &:= -4^4 - 6^0 - 3^2 + 6^6 - 5^2 \\ 46276 &:= -4^1 - 6^0 - 2^5 - 7^3 + 6^6 & 46329 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 2^0 - 9^2 & 46366 &:= -4^3 - 6^0 - 3^2 - 6^3 + 6^6 \\ 46278 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 7^1 - 8^0 & 46332 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 3^5 - 2^9 & 46367 &:= -4^4 + 6^0 - 3^3 + 6^6 - 7^1 \\ 46280 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 8^1 + 0^1 & 46333 &:= -4^5 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 3^6 - 3^3 & 46368 &:= -4^3 - 6^3 - 3^2 + 6^6 + 8^0 \\ 46281 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 8^1 + 1^0 & 46334 &:= -4^2 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 3^0 - 4^3 & 46369 &:= -4^5 - 6^0 + 3^2 + 6^6 + 9^3 \\ 46282 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 + 2^1 + 8^1 - 2^7 & 46335 &:= -4^5 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 3^6 - 5^2 & 46372 &:= -4^2 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 7^0 - 2^9 \\ 46283 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 8^1 + 3^1 & 46336 &:= -4^4 - 6^2 - 3^0 - 3^3 + 6^6 & 46372 &:= 4^7 + 6^5 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 2^7 \\ 46284 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 8^1 + 4^1 & 46337 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 + 3^0 + 3^3 - 7^3 & 46373 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 7^0 - 3^3 \\ 46285 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 + 2^1 + 8^1 - 5^3 & 46338 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 + 3^0 + 3^0 - 8^2 & 46373 &:= 4^7 + 6^5 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 3^9 \\ 46286 &:= -4^4 + 6^1 - 2^7 + 8^1 + 6^6 & 46342 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 4^0 - 2^3 & 46375 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 7^0 + 5^2 \\ 46287 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 2^7 + 8^1 + 7^1 & 46345 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 4^0 - 5^1 & 46376 &:= -4^2 - 6^3 + 3^0 - 7^2 + 6^6 \\ & & & & 46378 &:= -4^2 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 \\ & & & & 46379 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 7^1 - 9^0 \\ & & & & 46380 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 8^1 - 0^0 \end{aligned}$$

$46382 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 3^1 + 8^0 - 2^8$	$46421 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^1 + 2^4 + 1^0$	$46475 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 7^1 - 5^3$
$46383 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 8^0 - 3^5$	$46422 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 2^4$	$46480 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 8^2 + 0^1$
$46384 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 8^0 - 4^4$	$46423 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 4^4 + 2^8 - 3^6$	$46481 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 8^2 + 1^0$
$46385 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 8^0 - 5^2$	$46424 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 4^1 + 2^5 - 4^4$	$46482 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 8^2 + 2^1$
$46386 := -4^3 + 6^2 - 3^5 + 8^0 + 6^6$	$46425 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 4^4 + 2^2 + 5^2$	$46483 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 3^4$
$46388 := -4^5 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 8^0 + 8^3$	$46426 := -4^2 - 6^3 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 6^6$	$46484 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 4^2$
$46389 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 8^0 - 9^1$	$46427 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 4^4 + 2^5 - 7^0$	$46485 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 4^4 + 8^2 + 5^2$
$46391 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 3^2 + 9^0 - 1^0$	$46428 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 4^4 + 2^5 - 8^3$	$46486 := -4^4 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 8^2 + 6^6$
$46392 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 9^1 - 2^9$	$46429 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 4^4 + 2^5 + 9^0$	$46487 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 4^3 + 8^1 - 7^2$
$46393 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 3^0 + 9^0 - 3^2$	$46430 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^1 + 3^3 - 0^0$	$46488 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 8^2$
$46394 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 3^1 + 9^0 - 4^4$	$46432 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 3^0 + 2^5$	$46489 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 8^2 + 9^1$
$46395 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 9^1 - 5^3$	$46435 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 3^2 + 5^2$	$46495 := -4^5 - 6^0 + 4^6 + 9^5 - 5^6$
$46396 := -4^2 - 6^3 - 3^3 - 9^0 + 6^6$	$46436 := -4^1 - 6^3 + 4^0 - 3^0 + 6^6$	$46496 := -4^4 - 6^0 + 4^2 + 9^2 + 6^6$
$46397 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 9^0 - 7^0$	$46436 := -4^1 - 6^3 - 4^0 + 3^0 + 6^6$	$46498 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 9^2 + 8^0$
$46398 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 9^1 - 8^1$	$46437 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 3^7 - 7^4$	$46504 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 5^2 + 0^0 - 4^3$
$46399 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 9^0 + 9^0$	$46444 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 4^2 + 4^3 - 4^4$	$46508 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 0^0 - 8^1$
$46400 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 0^0 + 0^1$	$46445 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^1 + 4^2 + 5^2$	$46512 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 1^0 - 2^4$
$46401 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 0^0 + 1^0$	$46447 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 4^4 + 4^3 - 7^0$	$46513 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 1^0 - 3^1$
$46402 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 0^0 + 2^1$	$46448 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 4^4 - 8^3$	$46514 := -4^5 + 6^6 + 5^4 + 1^0 + 4^4$
$46403 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 0^0 + 3^0$	$46449 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 4^4 + 4^3 + 9^0$	$46515 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 1^0 - 5^3$
$46404 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 0^0 + 4^1$	$46453 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 5^2 + 3^3$	$46517 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 1^0 + 7^0$
$46405 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 0^0 + 5^1$	$46462 := -4^3 - 6^0 - 4^0 + 6^6 - 2^7$	$46518 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 1^0 - 8^1$
$46406 := -4^4 + 6^0 + 4^1 + 0^0 + 6^6$	$46464 := -4^4 + 6^0 - 4^0 + 6^6 + 4^3$	$46519 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 1^0 - 9^1$
$46407 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 0^0 + 7^1$	$46464 := -4^4 - 6^0 + 4^0 + 6^6 + 4^3$	$46520 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 2^2 + 0^0$
$46408 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 0^0 + 8^1$	$46465 := -4^1 - 6^3 + 4^1 + 6^6 + 5^2$	$46522 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 2^0 - 2^8$
$46409 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 4^0 + 0^0 + 9^1$	$46466 := -4^4 + 6^0 + 4^3 + 6^0 + 6^6$	$46523 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 2^0 - 3^5$
$46416 := -4^4 - 6^0 + 4^2 + 1^0 + 6^6$	$46469 := -4^4 + 6^1 + 4^3 + 6^6 - 9^0$	$46524 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 2^0 - 4^1$
$46418 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 1^0 + 8^0$	$46470 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 7^1 - 0^0$	$46525 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 2^0 + 5^3$
$46420 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 4^1 + 2^4 + 0^1$	$46472 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 7^3 - 2^9$	$46526 := -4^2 - 6^0 - 5^4 + 2^9 + 6^6$
		$46527 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 2^0 - 7^0$
		$46528 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 2^1 - 8^0$
		$46529 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 2^0 + 9^0$

$46530 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 0^1$	$46565 := -4^3 - 6^0 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 5^2$	$46604 := -4^2 - 6^2 + 6^6 - 0^0 + 4^0$
$46531 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 1^0$	$46567 := -4^2 + 6^0 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^2$	$46605 := -4^2 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 5^0$
$46532 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 3^2 - 2^7$	$46569 := -4^1 - 6^0 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 9^2$	$46606 := -4^2 + 6^0 - 6^2 + 0^0 + 6^6$
$46533 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 3^1$	$46572 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 7^2 - 2^7$	$46608 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 0^1 - 8^1$
$46534 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 4^1$	$46573 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 7^0 - 3^4$	$46613 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 1^0 - 3^3$
$46535 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 3^2 - 5^3$	$46575 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 7^2 - 5^3$	$46614 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 - 1^0 - 4^0$
$46536 := -4^1 + 6^1 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 6^6$	$46577 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 7^0 + 7^2$	$46615 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 1^0 - 5^2$
$46537 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 7^1$	$46578 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 7^0 - 8^2$	$46616 := -4^1 - 6^0 - 6^2 + 1^0 + 6^6$
$46538 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 8^1$	$46579 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 7^1 - 9^2$	$46618 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 8^0$
$46539 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 9^1$	$46580 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 8^2 + 0^0$	$46620 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 2^5 + 0^0$
$46540 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 4^2 - 0^0$	$46582 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 8^0 - 2^6$	$46621 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 2^2 + 1^0$
$46542 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 4^2 - 2^0$	$46583 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 8^0 - 3^2$	$46622 := -4^1 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 2^0 - 2^5$
$46543 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 4^0 + 3^3$	$46584 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^1 + 8^0 - 4^3$	$46623 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 2^0 - 3^3$
$46544 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 4^0 + 4^2$	$46586 := -4^1 - 6^0 - 5^0 - 8^2 + 6^6$	$46624 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 2^2 + 4^1$
$46549 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 5^4 + 4^0 - 9^3$	$46587 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^1 + 8^0 - 7^2$	$46625 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 2^0 - 5^2$
$46550 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 5^2 + 5^3 + 0^1$	$46588 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 8^0 - 8^2$	$46626 := -4^1 + 6^1 - 6^2 + 2^2 + 6^6$
$46551 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 5^2 - 1^0$	$46589 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 5^1 + 8^0 + 9^0$	$46627 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 2^2 + 7^1$
$46552 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^2 + 5^0 - 2^6$	$46591 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 9^0 - 1^0$	$46628 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 2^2 + 8^1$
$46553 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 5^4 - 3^6$	$46592 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^1 + 9^1 - 2^6$	$46629 := -4^1 - 6^1 + 6^6 - 2^3 - 9^1$
$46554 := -4^2 - 6^3 - 5^5 - 5^6 + 4^8$	$46593 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 5^2 + 9^1 - 3^4$	$46630 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^2 + 0^1$
$46555 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 5^2 + 5^3$	$46594 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 9^0 - 4^3$	$46631 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^2 + 1^0$
$46556 := -4^1 - 6^3 - 5^1 + 5^3 + 6^6$	$46595 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 9^2 - 5^3$	$46632 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^1 - 2^4$
$46557 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 5^2 + 5^3 + 7^1$	$46596 := -4^2 - 6^2 + 5^0 - 9^1 + 6^6$	$46633 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^2 - 3^2$
$46558 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 5^2 - 8^2$	$46597 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 9^0 - 7^2$	$46634 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^0 - 4^2$
$46559 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 5^0 - 9^2$	$46598 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 9^1 - 8^2$	$46635 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 3^2 - 5^2$
$46560 := -4^1 - 6^3 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 0^0$	$46599 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 9^2 - 9^1$	$46636 := -4^1 - 6^0 - 6^1 - 3^2 + 6^6$
$46562 := -4^1 - 6^0 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 2^6$	$46600 := -4^3 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 0^0 + 0^0$	$46637 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^0 - 7^0$
$46563 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 3^4$	$46602 := -4^2 - 6^1 + 6^6 + 0^1 - 2^5$	$46638 := -4^1 - 6^1 + 6^6 - 3^2 + 8^0$
$46564 := -4^1 + 6^0 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 4^3$	$46603 := -4^2 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 0^1 - 3^0$	$46639 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^1 - 9^1$
		$46640 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 0^1$
		$46641 := -4^1 - 6^1 + 6^6 - 4^1 - 1^0$
		$46642 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 4^0 - 2^3$

$46643 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 - 3^2$	$46674 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 4^2$	$46698 := -4^1 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 8^0$
$46644 := -4^1 - 6^1 + 6^6 - 4^0 - 4^0$	$46675 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 5^2$	$46700 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 0^1 - 0^0$
$46645 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 4^0 - 5^1$	$46675 := 4^2 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 5^0$	$46701 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 0^0 - 1^0$
$46646 := -4^1 - 6^0 - 6^0 - 4^1 + 6^6$	$46676 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^2 + 7^0 + 6^6$	$46702 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 0^1 + 2^0$
$46647 := -4^1 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 - 7^1$	$46678 := -4^2 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 8^0$	$46703 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 0^0 + 3^0$
$46648 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 4^1 + 8^0$	$46679 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^2 - 9^1$	$46704 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 0^0 + 4^3$
$46649 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 4^0 - 9^0$	$46680 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 0^1$	$46705 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 0^0 + 5^2$
$46650 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 0^1$	$46680 := 4^2 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 0^0$	$46706 := -4^4 - 6^2 + 7^3 - 0^0 + 6^6$
$46651 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 1^0$	$46681 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 1^0$	$46710 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 0^1$
$46652 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 2^1$	$46682 := 4^1 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 2^3$	$46711 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 1^0$
$46653 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 3^0$	$46682 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 8^0 + 2^5$	$46712 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 2^1$
$46654 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 4^1$	$46683 := 4^1 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 3^2$	$46712 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 2^6$
$46655 := -4^1 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 5^0$	$46683 := -4^1 - 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^2 - 3^3$	$46713 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 3^1$
$46656 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^1 - 5^0 + 6^6$	$46684 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 4^1$	$46714 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 4^1$
$46657 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 7^1$	$46685 := -4^1 - 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^2 - 5^2$	$46714 := -4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4 - 1^0 + 4^8$
$46658 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 8^1$	$46686 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^2 - 8^0 + 6^6$	$46715 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 5^1$
$46659 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 9^1$	$46687 := -4^1 - 6^1 + 6^6 - 8^1 + 7^2$	$46715 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 5^2$
$46660 := -4^1 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 0^0$	$46687 := 4^2 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 7^0$	$46716 := 4^1 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 6^6$
$46662 := -4^1 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 2^3$	$46688 := -4^1 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 8^0 - 8^0$	$46717 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 7^2$
$46663 := 4^1 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 3^0$	$46689 := -4^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 - 8^1 + 9^2$	$46718 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 8^2$
$46663 := -4^1 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 3^2$	$46690 := -4^1 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 0^0$	$46718 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 8^1$
$46665 := -4^1 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 5^0$	$46692 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 2^5$	$46719 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0 + 9^1$
$46668 := 4^1 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^0$	$46693 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 9^2 - 3^3$	$46720 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 2^5 - 0^0$
$46668 := -4^3 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^2$	$46694 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 4^3$	$46722 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^6 - 2^0$
$46669 := -4^2 - 6^1 + 6^2 + 6^6 - 9^0$	$46695 := 4^1 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 5^2$	$46723 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 3^4$
$46672 := 4^1 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^2$	$46695 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 9^2 + 5^3$	$46723 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 2^0 + 3^0$
$46672 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 2^5$	$46696 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 6^6$	$46724 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^0 + 4^3$
$46673 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^2 - 3^3$	$46697 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2$	$46724 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 2^1 + 4^0$
$46674 := 4^1 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 4^0$	$46698 := 4^1 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 8^0$	$46725 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^0 + 5^3$
		$46726 := 4^1 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 2^6 + 6^6$
		$46726 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 7^3 - 2^8 + 6^6$
		$46728 := -4^3 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^7 + 8^0$

$46729 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^0 + 9^2$	$46748 := -4^1 + 6^0 - 7^4 + 4^7 + 8^5$	$46776 := 4^2 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 6^6$
$46729 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 2^0 + 9^0$	$46749 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 4^0 + 9^2$	$46777 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 7^2 + 7^2$
$46730 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^2 + 0^1$	$46749 := -4^7 - 6^0 - 7^4 + 4^8 - 9^0$	$46778 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 8^1$
$46731 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 3^4 - 1^0$	$46752 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 5^3 - 2^5$	$46779 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 9^1$
$46731 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^2 + 1^0$	$46753 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 3^4$	$46782 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 2^7$
$46732 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 3^4 - 2^1$	$46753 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 5^2 + 3^3$	$46783 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 8^0 + 3^4$
$46732 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 3^0 + 2^6$	$46754 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 7^1 + 5^3 - 4^2$	$46785 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 8^0 + 5^3$
$46733 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 3^0 + 3^4$	$46757 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 5^3 - 7^1$	$46786 := 4^2 + 6^0 + 7^2 + 8^2 + 6^6$
$46733 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 3^3 + 3^3$	$46758 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 7^1 + 5^4 - 8^3$	$46790 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 0^1$
$46734 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$46759 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 5^2 + 9^2$	$46791 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 1^0$
$46735 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 3^4 + 5^0$	$46759 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 5^1 + 9^2$	$46792 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 2^1$
$46735 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 5^2$	$46760 := -4^3 + 6^3 - 7^2 + 6^6 + 0^0$	$46792 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 9^2 + 2^6$
$46736 := 4^2 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 3^2 + 6^6$	$46762 := -4^2 + 6^0 - 7^1 + 6^6 + 2^7$	$46793 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 3^1$
$46736 := -4^4 - 6^1 + 7^3 - 3^0 + 6^6$	$46764 := -4^1 - 6^0 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 4^3$	$46794 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 4^1$
$46737 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$46764 := 4^3 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 4^0$	$46795 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 5^3$
$46737 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 7^2 + 3^5 - 7^2$	$46765 := -4^2 + 6^0 - 7^0 + 6^6 + 5^3$	$46795 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 5^2$
$46738 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 8^2$	$46765 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 5^3$	$46796 := 4^1 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 6^6$
$46738 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 3^3 + 8^2$	$46766 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 7^3 - 6^3 + 6^6$	$46797 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 9^2 + 7^2$
$46739 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 3^4 - 9^0$	$46768 := -4^2 - 6^3 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 8^0$	$46798 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 9^2 + 8^2$
$46739 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^2 + 9^1$	$46769 := -4^2 - 6^0 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^2$	$46798 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 8^1$
$46742 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 4^0 + 2^5$	$46770 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 0^1$	$46799 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^1 + 9^2$
$46742 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 4^0 - 2^1$	$46771 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 1^0$	$46802 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 2^7$
$46743 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 3^4$	$46772 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 7^2 + 2^6$	$46803 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 3^4$
$46743 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 4^0 - 3^0$	$46772 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 2^1$	$46805 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 0^1 + 5^3$
$46744 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 4^0 + 4^3$	$46773 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 3^1$	$46807 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 0^1 + 7^3$
$46744 := -4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4 - 4^0 + 4^8$	$46774 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 7^2 + 4^3$	$46809 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 0^1 + 9^2$
$46745 := -4^4 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 4^0 + 5^0$	$46774 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 7^2 + 7^5 - 4^7$	$46809 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 8^3 + 0^1 + 9^3$
$46746 := 4^1 + 6^2 + 7^2 + 4^0 + 6^6$	$46775 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 5^2$	$46823 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 3^3$
$46746 := -4^4 - 6^0 + 7^3 + 4^1 + 6^6$	$46775 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 5^1$	$46823 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 2^8 - 3^4$
		$46824 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 4^2$
		$46824 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 8^1 + 2^7 + 4^3$
		$46825 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 5^3$

$$\begin{aligned} 46825 &:= -4^2 - 6^4 + 8^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 & 46859 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 5^3 + 9^2 & 46928 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 2^8 - 8^0 \\ 46826 &:= -4^2 - 6^1 + 8^2 + 2^7 + 6^6 & 46860 &:= -4^1 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 6^6 + 0^1 & 46930 &:= 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 0^1 \\ 46829 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 2^5 + 9^2 & 46861 &:= -4^1 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 6^6 + 1^0 & 46931 &:= 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 1^0 \\ 46830 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 - 8^2 + 3^5 - 0^0 & 46862 &:= -4^1 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 6^6 + 2^1 & 46932 &:= 4^2 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 2^8 \\ 46832 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 3^5 - 2^6 & 46862 &:= 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 2^7 & 46932 &:= -4^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^3 + 2^8 \\ 46833 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 8^0 + 3^5 - 3^0 & 46863 &:= -4^1 - 6^1 - 8^3 + 6^6 + 3^6 & 46933 &:= 4^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 3^5 \\ 46835 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 3^5 - 5^0 & 46863 &:= 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 3^7 & 46933 &:= -4^6 - 6^5 + 9^5 - 3^0 - 3^5 \\ 46835 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 8^0 + 3^5 + 5^0 & 46864 &:= -4^1 - 6^2 - 8^1 + 6^6 + 4^4 & 46934 &:= 4^1 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 4^4 \\ 46836 &:= -4^3 + 6^3 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 6^6 & 46865 &:= -4^1 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 6^6 + 5^1 & 46934 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 - 9^0 + 3^3 + 4^4 \\ 46837 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 3^5 + 7^0 & 46866 &:= -4^1 - 6^0 - 8^0 + 6^3 + 6^6 & 46935 &:= 4^3 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^4 + 5^3 \\ 46840 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 8^1 + 4^4 + 0^1 & 46867 &:= -4^1 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 6^6 + 7^1 & 46935 &:= -4^6 - 6^5 + 9^5 - 3^5 + 5^0 \\ 46841 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 8^1 + 4^4 + 1^0 & 46868 &:= -4^1 + 6^3 + 8^0 + 6^6 - 8^0 & 46936 &:= -4^2 + 6^3 - 9^0 + 3^4 + 6^6 \\ 46842 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 - 8^2 + 4^4 - 2^1 & 46868 &:= -4^1 + 6^3 - 8^0 + 6^6 + 8^0 & 46936 &:= 4^4 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 6^6 \\ 46843 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 - 8^2 + 4^4 - 3^0 & 46869 &:= -4^1 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 6^6 + 9^1 & 46937 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 7^3 \\ 46843 &:= 4^2 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 3^7 & 46870 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 8^2 + 7^3 - 0^0 & 46937 &:= 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 7^1 \\ 46844 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 4^3 + 4^3 & 46872 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 7^3 - 2^6 & 46938 &:= -4^2 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 3^5 + 8^2 \\ 46845 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 4^1 + 5^3 & 46876 &:= -4^1 + 6^3 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 6^6 & 46938 &:= 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 8^1 \\ 46846 &:= -4^3 - 6^0 - 8^0 + 4^4 + 6^6 & 46883 &:= -4^2 + 6^6 - 8^0 + 8^0 + 3^5 & 46939 &:= 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 9^1 \\ 46847 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 8^1 + 4^4 + 7^1 & 46893 &:= -4^2 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 3^5 & 46945 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 9^2 + 4^0 + 5^4 \\ 46848 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 4^4 - 8^0 & 46912 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 - 9^0 + 1^0 + 2^9 & 46946 &:= -4^1 - 6^0 - 9^3 + 4^5 + 6^6 \\ 46848 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 8^0 + 4^4 + 8^0 & 46913 &:= 4^1 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 3^5 & 46946 &:= 4^3 + 6^3 + 9^1 + 4^0 + 6^6 \\ 46849 &:= -4^2 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 4^3 + 9^2 & 46915 &:= 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 & 46948 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 - 9^3 + 4^5 + 8^0 \\ 46849 &:= 4^3 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 4^3 + 9^0 & 46920 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 2^9 - 0^0 & 46952 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 - 9^2 + 5^3 + 2^8 \\ 46850 &:= 4^1 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 5^3 + 0^0 & 46922 &:= 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 2^3 & 46953 &:= -4^1 + 6^6 - 9^2 + 5^4 - 3^5 \\ 46852 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 8^0 + 5^1 + 2^8 & 46922 &:= -4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 2^0 + 2^9 & 46953 &:= 4^3 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 5^3 + 3^3 \\ 46854 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 4^4 & 46923 &:= 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 3^2 & 46954 &:= 4^2 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 5^2 + 4^4 \\ 46854 &:= 4^3 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 5^3 + 4^0 & 46924 &:= 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 2^1 + 4^0 & 46954 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 5^2 + 4^4 \\ 46856 &:= -4^2 + 6^3 - 8^0 + 5^0 + 6^6 & 46926 &:= 4^1 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 2^8 + 6^6 & 46956 &:= -4^6 - 6^3 + 9^5 - 5^1 - 6^5 \\ 46858 &:= -4^5 + 6^0 - 8^3 + 5^6 + 8^5 & 46927 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 2^0 + 7^3 & 46959 &:= 4^2 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 5^3 + 9^2 \\ & & & & 46960 &:= -4^6 - 6^3 + 9^5 - 6^5 - 0^0 \\ & & & & 46962 &:= -4^6 - 6^3 + 9^5 - 6^5 + 2^0 \\ & & & & 46963 &:= -4^2 - 6^0 + 9^2 + 6^6 + 3^5 \end{aligned}$$

$46966 := -4^4 - 6^0 - 9^3 + 6^4 + 6^6$	$47046 := -4^2 + 7^3 - 0^0 + 4^3 + 6^6$	$47328 := -4^3 + 7^5 - 3^7 + 2^2 + 8^5$
$46968 := -4^4 + 6^4 - 9^3 + 6^6 + 8^0$	$47062 := -4^3 + 7^3 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 2^7$	$47346 := -4^2 - 7^1 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^6$
$46970 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 0^1$	$47063 := -4^2 + 7^3 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 3^4$	$47346 := 4^3 + 7^3 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 6^6$
$46971 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 1^0$	$47064 := -4^2 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 6^6 - 4^7$	$47361 := -4^2 - 7^1 + 3^6 + 6^6 - 1^0$
$46972 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^3 - 2^5$	$47064 := 4^3 + 7^3 + 0^1 + 6^6 + 4^0$	$47362 := -4^2 + 7^0 + 3^6 + 6^6 - 2^3$
$46972 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 2^1$	$47065 := 4^3 + 7^3 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 5^0$	$47362 := 4^3 + 7^2 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 2^9$
$46973 := 4^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 3^5$	$47068 := 4^1 + 7^3 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 8^2$	$47363 := -4^2 - 7^1 + 3^0 + 6^6 + 3^6$
$46973 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 9^0 + 7^3 - 3^2$	$47069 := -4^7 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 6^6 - 9^1$	$47363 := 4^4 + 7^3 + 3^3 + 6^6 + 3^4$
$46974 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 4^4$	$47086 := -4^7 + 7^5 - 0^0 + 8^1 + 6^6$	$47364 := -4^1 - 7^0 + 3^6 + 6^6 - 4^2$
$46975 := -4^2 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 7^3 + 5^0$	$47096 := 4^2 + 7^3 + 0^1 + 9^2 + 6^6$	$47365 := -4^1 + 7^1 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 5^4$
$46975 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 7^2 + 5^3$	$47162 := -4^1 - 7^0 - 1^0 + 6^6 + 2^9$	$47367 := -4^1 - 7^1 + 3^6 + 6^6 - 7^1$
$46976 := 4^2 + 6^3 + 9^2 + 7^1 + 6^6$	$47163 := 4^4 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 3^5$	$47367 := 4^2 + 7^3 + 3^2 + 6^6 + 7^3$
$46976 := -4^2 - 6^1 - 9^0 + 7^3 + 6^6$	$47169 := -4^6 - 7^1 - 1^0 - 6^5 + 9^5$	$47368 := -4^2 + 7^1 + 3^6 + 6^6 - 8^1$
$46977 := -4^2 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 7^3 - 7^1$	$47186 := 4^2 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 8^3 + 6^6$	$47368 := 4^4 + 7^1 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 8^5$
$46977 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 7^2$	$47236 := -4^1 + 7^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 6^6$	$47369 := -4^2 + 7^0 - 3^0 + 6^6 + 9^3$
$46978 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 7^3 - 8^1$	$47236 := 4^2 + 7^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 6^6$	$47369 := -4^2 - 7^0 + 3^0 + 6^6 + 9^3$
$46978 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 8^2$	$47256 := 4^1 + 7^3 + 2^7 + 5^3 + 6^6$	$47382 := -4^1 + 7^5 - 3^7 + 8^5 - 2^1$
$46979 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 9^1$	$47256 := -4^1 + 7^3 + 2^8 + 5^1 + 6^6$	$47383 := -4^1 + 7^5 - 3^0 + 8^5 - 3^7$
$46986 := 4^4 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 8^2 + 6^6$	$47260 := 4^1 + 7^3 + 2^8 + 6^6 + 0^0$	$47385 := -4^1 + 7^5 - 3^7 + 8^5 + 5^0$
$46987 := -4^1 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 8^0 + 7^3$	$47264 := 4^4 + 7^3 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 4^0$	$47386 := -4^3 + 7^0 + 3^6 + 8^2 + 6^6$
$46992 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 9^0 + 9^2 + 2^9$	$47264 := -4^7 - 7^4 + 2^9 + 6^0 + 4^8$	$47388 := -4^3 + 7^5 - 3^7 + 8^2 + 8^5$
$46993 := 4^1 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 9^2 + 3^5$	$47265 := -4^2 + 7^0 - 2^0 + 6^6 + 5^4$	$47416 := -4^2 - 7^5 + 4^8 - 1^0 - 6^4$
$46994 := 4^3 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 9^1 + 4^4$	$47265 := -4^2 - 7^0 + 2^0 + 6^6 + 5^4$	$47426 := 4^4 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 2^9 + 6^6$
$46995 := 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 9^2 + 5^0$	$47276 := -4^3 + 7^3 - 2^1 + 7^3 + 6^6$	$47426 := -4^4 + 7^0 + 4^5 + 2^0 + 6^6$
$46995 := -4^4 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 9^3 - 5^3$	$47296 := -4^3 + 7^1 - 2^5 + 9^3 + 6^6$	$47445 := -4^3 - 7^4 - 4^0 + 4^8 - 5^6$
$46997 := -4^1 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 7^3$	$47296 := 4^4 + 7^3 + 2^5 + 9^1 + 6^6$	$47448 := -4^4 - 7^5 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 8^0$
$47016 := 4^2 + 7^3 + 0^1 + 1^0 + 6^6$	$47306 := 4^3 + 7^3 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 6^6$	$47452 := -4^5 - 7^5 + 4^8 - 5^3 - 2^7$
$47026 := -4^1 + 7^3 - 0^0 + 2^5 + 6^6$	$47324 := -4^7 + 7^3 - 3^7 + 2^4 + 4^8$	$47454 := -4^4 - 7^5 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 4^8$
$47026 := 4^3 + 7^2 + 0^0 + 2^8 + 6^6$	$47326 := -4^3 + 7^0 + 3^6 + 2^2 + 6^6$	$47455 := -4^5 - 7^5 + 4^8 - 5^3 - 5^3$
		$47456 := -4^3 + 7^5 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^4$
		$47457 := -4^1 - 7^2 + 4^8 - 5^6 - 7^4$
		$47458 := -4^6 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 8^5$

$47463 := -4^5 - 7^5 + 4^8 + 6^0 - 3^5$	$47639 := 4^1 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 9^3$	$47697 := 4^4 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 7^2$
$47473 := -4^7 - 7^1 + 4^8 - 7^4 + 3^6$	$47642 := -4^5 - 7^5 + 6^0 + 4^8 - 2^6$	$47697 := -4^7 - 7^3 + 6^5 + 9^5 - 7^4$
$47475 := -4^7 - 7^4 + 4^8 - 7^4 + 5^5$	$47643 := 4^4 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 3^6$	$47698 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 8^1$
$47478 := -4^5 - 7^2 - 4^5 + 7^5 + 8^5$	$47646 := -4^4 - 7^2 + 6^4 - 4^0 + 6^6$	$47699 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 9^3$
$47479 := -4^7 - 7^0 + 4^8 - 7^4 + 9^3$	$47649 := 4^4 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 9^3$	$47704 := -4^5 - 7^0 - 7^5 + 0^1 + 4^8$
$47495 := -4^2 - 7^4 + 4^8 + 9^0 - 5^6$	$47652 := -4^1 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 5^4 + 2^5$	$47726 := 4^4 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 2^7 + 6^6$
$47526 := -4^1 - 7^1 + 5^4 + 2^8 + 6^6$	$47652 := 4^2 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 2^9$	$47743 := -4^4 - 7^0 - 7^5 + 4^8 - 3^6$
$47543 := -4^7 - 7^0 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 3^7$	$47653 := 4^4 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 3^6$	$47745 := -4^2 - 7^3 - 7^5 + 4^8 - 5^4$
$47546 := -4^2 + 7^1 - 5^3 + 4^5 + 6^6$	$47656 := -4^1 + 7^3 + 6^2 + 5^4 + 6^6$	$47746 := 4^2 + 7^0 + 7^2 + 4^5 + 6^6$
$47560 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 0^1$	$47657 := -4^2 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 5^4 + 7^3$	$47747 := -4^5 - 7^1 + 7^2 + 4^8 - 7^5$
$47561 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 1^0$	$47658 := -4^3 + 7^4 - 6^2 + 5^7 - 8^5$	$47762 := 4^5 + 7^0 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 2^5$
$47562 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 2^1$	$47663 := -4^3 + 7^3 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 3^6$	$47763 := 4^5 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 3^4$
$47563 := 4^1 + 7^2 + 5^3 + 6^6 + 3^6$	$47664 := -4^2 + 7^0 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 4^5$	$47763 := -4^5 - 7^1 - 7^2 + 6^6 + 3^7$
$47563 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 3^1$	$47664 := -4^2 - 7^0 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 4^5$	$47766 := 4^5 + 7^0 + 7^2 + 6^2 + 6^6$
$47564 := -4^3 + 7^0 - 5^5 + 6^6 + 4^6$	$47673 := 4^6 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 3^7$	$47768 := 4^4 + 7^0 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 8^3$
$47565 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 + 5^4$	$47674 := -4^1 - 7^0 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 4^5$	$47769 := 4^5 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 9^2$
$47566 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^1 + 6^6$	$47679 := 4^4 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 9^2$	$47784 := -4^5 - 7^0 - 7^3 + 8^5 + 4^7$
$47567 := -4^3 + 7^1 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 7^3$	$47683 := 4^5 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 3^0$	$47786 := 4^5 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 6^6$
$47568 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^1$	$47684 := -4^1 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 4^5$	$47823 := -4^5 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 2^0 - 3^6$
$47569 := -4^3 + 7^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 9^1$	$47689 := 4^5 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 9^0$	$47835 := -4^1 + 7^4 - 8^5 + 3^4 + 5^7$
$47583 := -4^5 + 7^4 + 5^6 + 8^5 - 3^7$	$47690 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 0^1$	$47855 := -4^4 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 5^6 - 5^4$
$47585 := -4^7 - 7^2 + 5^6 + 8^5 + 5^6$	$47691 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 1^0$	$47858 := -4^2 - 7^1 - 8^3 + 5^6 + 8^5$
$47586 := -4^4 + 7^2 + 5^4 + 8^3 + 6^6$	$47692 := -4^1 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 9^3 - 2^5$	$47872 := -4^6 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 7^5 - 2^3$
$47606 := -4^1 - 7^3 + 6^4 + 0^0 + 6^6$	$47692 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 2^1$	$47874 := -4^5 - 7^3 + 8^3 - 7^5 + 4^8$
$47614 := -4^2 - 7^2 + 6^6 - 1^0 + 4^5$	$47693 := 4^2 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 3^5$	$47875 := -4^6 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 7^5 - 5^1$
$47624 := -4^3 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 2^0 + 4^5$	$47694 := 4^1 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 4^5$	$47879 := -4^6 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 7^5 - 9^0$
$47632 := -4^2 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 3^6 + 2^8$	$47695 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3 + 5^1$	$47944 := 4^6 + 7^5 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 4^7$
$47633 := 4^1 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 3^6$	$47696 := 4^4 + 7^2 + 6^1 + 9^3 + 6^6$	$47946 := 4^4 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 4^5 + 6^6$
$47635 := -4^2 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 3^3 + 5^4$	$47696 := -4^4 - 7^0 + 6^4 + 9^0 + 6^6$	$47947 := -4^1 - 7^2 - 9^3 + 4^8 - 7^5$
		$47962 := 4^2 + 7^2 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 2^9$
		$47965 := -4^3 + 7^6 + 9^3 + 6^5 - 5^7$
		$47966 := 4^1 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 6^4 + 6^6$

$47967 := 4^2 + 7^5 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 7^5$	$48329 := -4^3 - 8^4 - 3^8 + 2^0 + 9^5$	$48390 := -4^6 - 8^0 - 3^8 + 9^5 - 0^0$
$47968 := 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 8^3$	$48332 := -4^6 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 3^9 - 2^5$	$48392 := -4^1 - 8^4 - 3^8 + 9^5 + 2^2$
$47968 := -4^5 + 7^4 - 9^0 + 6^6 - 8^2$	$48333 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 3^8 + 3^8$	$48393 := -4^6 - 8^1 + 3^2 + 9^5 - 3^8$
$47985 := -4^3 - 7^3 - 9^0 + 8^5 + 5^6$	$48334 := -4^7 - 8^1 - 3^4 - 3^6 + 4^8$	$48394 := -4^6 + 8^0 - 3^8 + 9^5 + 4^0$
$48017 := -4^8 - 8^4 + 0^0 - 1^0 + 7^6$	$48335 := -4^1 + 8^5 - 3^4 + 3^3 + 5^6$	$48395 := -4^1 + 8^5 - 3^1 + 9^1 + 5^6$
$48017 := -4^8 - 8^4 - 0^0 + 1^0 + 7^6$	$48336 := -4^1 - 8^3 + 3^2 + 3^7 + 6^6$	$48396 := -4^2 - 8^3 + 3^7 + 9^2 + 6^6$
$48096 := -4^5 - 8^4 - 0^0 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$48338 := -4^2 - 8^4 - 3^0 + 3^9 + 8^5$	$48396 := 4^4 + 8^3 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^6$
$48097 := -4^8 - 8^4 - 0^0 + 9^2 + 7^6$	$48343 := -4^7 + 8^0 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 3^6$	$48399 := -4^6 + 8^1 - 3^0 + 9^5 - 9^4$
$48152 := -4^4 + 8^5 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 2^4$	$48346 := -4^3 + 8^0 + 3^6 + 4^5 + 6^6$	$48405 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 0^1 + 5^6$
$48154 := -4^4 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 4^2$	$48348 := -4^6 - 8^1 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 8^5$	$48423 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 2^2 - 3^6$
$48224 := -4^5 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 2^6 + 4^7$	$48350 := -4^2 + 8^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 0^1$	$48425 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 2^5 + 5^6$
$48226 := 4^5 + 8^3 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 6^6$	$48351 := -4^2 + 8^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 1^0$	$48426 := -4^7 - 8^3 + 4^8 + 2^1 - 6^3$
$48243 := -4^5 + 8^5 - 2^7 + 4^7 + 3^5$	$48352 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 2^6$	$48433 := -4^7 + 8^0 + 4^8 + 3^2 - 3^6$
$48245 := -4^5 + 8^5 - 2^3 + 4^7 + 5^3$	$48353 := -4^1 + 8^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 3^3$	$48436 := 4^5 + 8^3 + 4^0 + 3^5 + 6^6$
$48248 := -4^5 - 8^1 + 2^7 + 4^7 + 8^5$	$48354 := -4^2 + 8^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 4^1$	$48445 := -4^2 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 4^3 + 5^6$
$48250 := -4^2 + 8^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 0^0$	$48355 := -4^1 + 8^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 5^2$	$48448 := -4^4 + 8^2 - 4^7 + 4^8 - 8^3$
$48254 := -4^5 + 8^5 + 2^0 + 5^3 + 4^7$	$48356 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$48452 := -4^1 + 8^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 2^6$
$48263 := -4^1 - 8^2 - 2^9 + 6^6 + 3^7$	$48357 := -4^1 + 8^5 - 3^4 + 5^6 + 7^2$	$48454 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 4^3$
$48264 := 4^3 + 8^1 + 2^9 + 6^6 + 4^5$	$48358 := -4^2 + 8^1 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 8^5$	$48455 := -4^3 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 5^6$
$48267 := -4^8 - 8^4 + 2^8 - 6^1 + 7^6$	$48359 := -4^2 + 8^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 9^1$	$48458 := 4^7 + 8^0 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 8^2$
$48272 := -4^8 - 8^4 - 2^0 + 7^6 + 2^8$	$48360 := -4^6 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 6^1 - 0^0$	$48459 := -4^2 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 9^2$
$48274 := -4^6 + 8^0 + 2^8 + 7^6 - 4^8$	$48362 := -4^6 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 6^1 + 2^0$	$48459 := 4^3 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 9^0$
$48276 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 2^0 + 7^5 - 6^4$	$48372 := -4^5 + 8^5 - 3^5 + 7^5 + 2^6$	$48464 := 4^2 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 6^6 + 4^5$
$48283 := -4^3 - 8^4 - 2^3 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$48375 := -4^2 + 8^5 - 3^1 + 7^0 + 5^6$	$48465 := -4^5 - 8^5 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 5^7$
$48287 := -4^5 - 8^1 - 2^8 + 8^5 + 7^5$	$48376 := -4^1 - 8^3 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 6^6$	$48469 := -4^1 + 8^2 + 4^5 + 6^6 + 9^3$
$48294 := -4^7 - 8^0 - 2^7 - 9^3 + 4^8$	$48378 := -4^8 - 8^5 + 3^7 - 7^6 + 8^6$	$48470 := -4^5 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 0^0$
$48307 := -4^6 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 0^0 - 7^2$	$48383 := -4^6 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$48471 := -4^4 - 8^0 + 4^8 - 7^5 - 1^0$
$48316 := -4^2 - 8^3 + 3^7 + 1^0 + 6^6$	$48385 := -4^1 - 8^0 - 3^1 + 8^5 + 5^6$	$48472 := -4^5 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 2^0$
$48326 := -4^1 - 8^0 + 3^7 - 2^9 + 6^6$	$48389 := -4^1 - 8^4 - 3^8 + 8^0 + 9^5$	$48473 := -4^4 - 8^0 + 4^8 - 7^5 + 3^0$
		$48475 := -4^8 - 8^3 - 4^0 + 7^6 - 5^5$
		$48483 := -4^1 + 8^2 + 4^7 + 8^5 - 3^6$
		$48485 := -4^6 - 8^7 - 4^8 + 8^6 + 5^9$

$48487 := -4^5 - 8^2 + 4^8 - 8^5 + 7^5$	$48573 := -4^3 + 8^5 - 5^5 + 7^5 + 3^7$	$48655 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^1 + 5^6$
$48507 := 4^3 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 7^2$	$48575 := -4^5 + 8^5 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 5^2$	$48656 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$48514 := -4^7 - 8^3 - 5^3 - 1^0 + 4^8$	$48577 := -4^5 + 8^5 + 5^2 + 7^0 + 7^5$	$48657 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 7^1$
$48515 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 1^0 + 5^6$	$48578 := -4^8 - 8^2 + 5^4 + 7^6 - 8^4$	$48657 := -4^5 - 8^0 + 6^6 + 5^4 + 7^4$
$48522 := 4^3 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 2^0 + 2^6$	$48584 := -4^3 - 8^0 + 5^6 + 8^5 + 4^4$	$48658 := 4^4 + 8^1 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 8^5$
$48524 := -4^1 + 8^5 - 5^4 + 2^0 + 4^7$	$48593 := -4^7 - 8^1 - 5^4 + 9^5 + 3^8$	$48659 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 9^1$
$48526 := 4^1 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 2^7 + 6^0$	$48594 := -4^3 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 9^1 + 4^4$	$48663 := -4^3 + 8^4 - 6^4 + 6^6 - 3^6$
$48527 := -4^5 + 8^5 - 5^2 + 2^0 + 7^5$	$48595 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 9^2 + 5^6$	$48664 := 4^4 + 8^3 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 4^5$
$48528 := -4^7 + 8^5 - 5^4 + 2^0 + 8^5$	$48596 := -4^3 + 8^3 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 6^5$	$48667 := 4^1 + 8^5 + 6^5 + 6^5 + 7^3$
$48532 := -4^2 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 3^3 + 2^7$	$48604 := -4^7 - 8^3 - 6^2 + 0^1 + 4^8$	$48669 := -4^1 - 8^1 + 6^4 + 6^6 + 9^3$
$48533 := -4^3 + 8^5 - 5^5 + 3^9 - 3^6$	$48605 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 5^6$	$48672 := -4^4 - 8^0 + 6^6 + 7^4 - 2^7$
$48534 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 3^4 + 4^3$	$48609 := -4^6 - 8^3 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 9^4$	$48675 := -4^4 - 8^0 + 6^6 + 7^4 - 5^3$
$48535 := 4^2 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 3^0 + 5^6$	$48624 := -4^7 + 8^3 - 6^4 + 2^8 + 4^8$	$48684 := -4^7 - 8^3 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 4^8$
$48535 := -4^3 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 3^4 + 5^6$	$48625 := -4^2 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 2^5 + 5^6$	$48685 := -4^1 + 8^3 - 6^3 + 8^5 + 5^6$
$48536 := -4^1 - 8^3 + 5^5 - 3^6 + 6^6$	$48625 := 4^5 + 8^2 + 6^6 + 2^8 + 5^4$	$48687 := -4^7 - 8^5 - 6^6 + 8^6 - 7^6$
$48539 := -4^2 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 3^4 + 9^2$	$48637 := -4^4 + 8^0 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 7^2$	$48704 := -4^2 - 8^1 - 7^5 - 0^0 + 4^8$
$48539 := 4^3 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 9^2$	$48640 := -4^7 - 8^3 + 6^0 + 4^8 - 0^0$	$48733 := -4^7 - 8^5 + 7^6 - 3^4 - 3^9$
$48542 := -4^7 - 8^0 - 5^4 + 4^8 + 2^4$	$48640 := -4^7 - 8^3 - 6^0 + 4^8 + 0^0$	$48734 := -4^1 + 8^1 - 7^5 + 3^0 + 4^8$
$48544 := -4^7 + 8^0 - 5^4 + 4^2 + 4^8$	$48642 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 6^1 + 4^7 - 2^9$	$48735 := -4^1 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 3^1 + 5^6$
$48546 := -4^3 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 4^0 + 6^3$	$48643 := -4^4 - 8^1 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 3^7$	$48736 := -4^4 - 8^2 + 7^4 - 3^0 + 6^6$
$48547 := -4^5 + 8^5 - 5^1 + 4^0 + 7^5$	$48645 := -4^5 - 8^5 + 6^3 + 4^6 + 5^7$	$48738 := -4^8 - 8^1 + 7^6 + 3^6 - 8^4$
$48549 := -4^7 + 8^0 + 5^3 + 4^8 - 9^3$	$48647 := -4^7 - 8^3 + 6^1 + 4^8 + 7^0$	$48742 := -4^1 + 8^0 - 7^5 + 4^8 + 2^4$
$48554 := -4^5 - 8^5 + 5^3 + 5^7 + 4^6$	$48649 := -4^7 + 8^2 - 6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3$	$48744 := -4^3 - 8^0 - 7^3 - 4^7 + 4^8$
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$48559 := -4^1 - 8^5 + 5^5 + 5^7 + 9^2$	$48651 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 1^0$	$48752 := -4^2 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 5^6 + 2^5$
$48562 := 4^5 + 8^0 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 2^8$	$48652 := 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 2^1$	$48753 := 4^2 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 5^6 + 3^0$
$48563 := -4^4 + 8^0 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 3^7$	$48653 := 4^2 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 3^5$	$48753 := -4^3 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 5^6 + 3^4$
$48564 := -4^7 + 8^0 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 4^8$	$48653 := -4^3 - 8^0 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^7$	$48754 := -4^3 + 8^2 - 7^5 + 5^2 + 4^8$
$48572 := -4^5 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 2^4$	$48654 := 4^1 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 4^4$	$48755 := -4^4 + 8^5 - 7^1 + 5^4 + 5^6$

$48766 := -4^4 + 8^0 + 7^4 + 6^6 - 6^2$	$48976 := -4^2 - 8^2 - 9^0 + 7^4 + 6^6$	$49219 := -4^7 + 9^4 - 2^3 + 1^0 + 9^5$
$48768 := -4^5 + 8^0 + 7^5 + 6^3 + 8^5$	$48977 := -4^4 + 8^5 + 9^0 + 7^5 - 7^3$	$49223 := -4^7 + 9^5 - 2^2 + 2^0 + 3^8$
$48776 := -4^8 + 8^4 + 7^3 + 7^6 - 6^5$	$48978 := -4^1 - 8^3 - 9^2 + 7^5 + 8^5$	$49224 := -4^7 + 9^1 - 2^0 + 2^6 + 4^8$
$48783 := -4^3 + 8^0 + 7^5 + 8^5 - 3^6$	$48995 := -4^1 - 8^5 - 9^5 + 9^6 - 5^8$	$49229 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 9^5$
$48794 := -4^2 + 8^5 - 7^3 + 9^0 + 4^7$	$48999 := -4^5 + 8^4 - 9^4 + 9^5 - 9^4$	$49230 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 0^1$
$48798 := -4^4 - 8^3 + 7^5 - 9^1 + 8^5$	$49024 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 0^0 - 2^7 + 4^8$	$49231 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 1^0$
$48799 := -4^6 + 8^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 - 9^4$	$49043 := -4^7 - 9^2 - 0^0 + 4^8 - 3^3$	$49232 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 2^2$
$48807 := -4^4 - 8^3 + 8^5 + 0^1 + 7^5$	$49045 := -4^7 - 9^2 - 0^0 + 4^8 - 5^2$	$49233 := -4^7 + 9^5 - 2^1 + 3^2 + 3^8$
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$48836 := -4^2 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 3^7 + 6^6$	$49064 := -4^7 - 9^2 - 0^0 - 6^1 + 4^8$	$49236 := 4^4 + 9^1 + 2^7 + 3^7 + 6^6$
$48845 := -4^3 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 5^6$	$49083 := -4^6 + 9^3 - 0^0 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$49236 := -4^6 + 9^4 - 2^7 + 3^5 + 6^6$
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$48864 := -4^3 - 8^1 + 8^5 - 6^3 + 4^7$	$49142 := -4^7 - 9^0 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 2^3$	$49238 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1$
$48865 := -4^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 5^6$	$49143 := -4^7 + 9^0 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 3^2$	$49239 := -4^7 + 9^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 9^5$
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$48894 := -4^4 - 8^0 + 8^5 - 9^0 + 4^7$	$49144 := -4^2 + 9^1 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 4^7$	$49242 := -4^7 + 9^2 + 2^0 + 4^8 + 2^3$
$48932 := -4^7 + 8^4 + 9^5 + 3^7 - 2^4$	$49145 := -4^7 - 9^0 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 5^1$	$49243 := -4^7 + 9^1 + 2^0 + 4^8 + 3^4$
$48936 := 4^1 + 8^1 + 9^2 + 3^7 + 6^6$	$49146 := -4^7 + 9^0 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 6^1$	$49248 := -4^7 + 9^2 + 2^4 + 4^8 - 8^0$
$48939 := -4^7 + 8^4 - 9^1 + 3^7 + 9^5$	$49146 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 1^0 + 4^8 - 6^1$	$49253 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 5^2 + 3^8$
$48942 := -4^7 - 8^0 - 9^2 + 4^8 - 2^7$	$49147 := -4^7 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 4^8 - 7^1$	$49254 := -4^3 - 9^2 - 2^9 - 5^6 + 4^8$
$48945 := -4^7 - 8^0 - 9^2 + 4^8 - 5^3$	$49148 := -4^1 + 9^0 - 1^0 + 4^7 + 8^5$	$49256 := -4^1 - 9^1 - 2^9 + 5^5 + 6^6$
$48946 := -4^7 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 4^8 - 6^3$	$49148 := -4^1 - 9^0 + 1^0 + 4^7 + 8^5$	$49259 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^3 + 5^2 + 9^5$
$48953 := -4^3 - 8^4 + 9^5 + 5^4 - 3^8$	$49149 := -4^7 - 9^0 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 9^0$	$49263 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 6^2 + 3^8$
$48954 := -4^7 - 8^2 - 9^1 - 5^3 + 4^8$	$49168 := 4^7 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 6^1 + 8^5$	$49273 := -4^7 + 9^5 - 2^1 + 7^2 + 3^8$
$48955 := -4^3 + 8^5 + 9^0 + 5^4 + 5^6$	$49186 := -4^6 + 9^4 + 1^0 + 8^2 + 6^6$	$49274 := -4^7 + 9^1 + 2^6 + 7^2 + 4^8$
$48956 := -4^1 + 8^5 - 9^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$49214 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 2^6 - 1^0 + 4^8$	$49278 := -4^4 - 9^1 - 2^5 + 7^5 + 8^5$
$48974 := -4^7 - 8^3 - 9^1 + 7^3 + 4^8$	$49218 := 4^7 + 9^0 + 2^6 + 1^0 + 8^5$	$49279 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^2 + 7^2 + 9^5$
		$49282 := 4^7 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 2^7$
		$49289 := -4^7 + 9^4 - 2^0 + 8^2 + 9^5$
		$49290 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^6 + 9^5 + 0^1$

$49291 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^6 + 9^5 + 1^0$	$49446 := -4^7 - 9^3 + 4^5 + 4^8 - 6^0$	$49647 := -4^8 - 9^4 - 6^0 + 4^6 + 7^6$
$49292 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^1 + 9^5 + 2^6$	$49448 := -4^7 - 9^3 + 4^5 + 4^8 + 8^0$	$49648 := -4^5 - 9^2 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 8^4$
$49293 := -4^5 - 9^4 + 2^4 + 9^5 - 3^7$	$49452 := -4^7 - 9^2 + 4^8 + 5^3 + 2^8$	$49652 := -4^2 - 9^2 + 6^6 + 5^5 - 2^5$
$49294 := -4^7 + 9^4 + 2^2 + 9^5 + 4^3$	$49453 := -4^7 - 9^2 + 4^8 + 5^4 - 3^5$	$49654 := -4^3 + 9^0 + 6^6 + 5^5 - 4^3$
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$49298 := 4^7 + 9^0 + 2^6 + 9^2 + 8^5$	$49478 := -4^2 - 9^0 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^5$	$49675 := -4^2 + 9^1 + 6^6 + 7^4 + 5^4$
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$49323 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 2^4 + 3^8$	$49498 := 4^4 + 9^1 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 8^5$	$49685 := -4^2 - 9^2 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 5^5$
$49324 := -4^7 - 9^2 - 3^1 + 2^8 + 4^8$	$49524 := -4^7 - 9^1 + 5^3 + 2^8 + 4^8$	$49689 := -4^6 - 9^4 + 6^4 + 8^0 + 9^5$
$49326 := -4^2 + 9^5 - 3^7 + 2^8 - 6^5$	$49526 := -4^4 - 9^0 + 5^5 + 2^1 + 6^6$	$49692 := -4^6 - 9^4 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 2^2$
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$49347 := -4^7 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 4^8 - 7^2$	$49542 := -4^4 - 9^2 - 5^6 + 4^8 - 2^5$	$49725 := -4^8 + 9^3 + 7^6 + 2^3 - 5^5$
$49350 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 0^0$	$49543 := -4^7 + 9^1 + 5^4 + 4^8 - 3^5$	$49726 := -4^3 + 9^3 + 7^4 + 2^2 + 6^6$
$49352 := -4^7 + 9^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 2^0$	$49548 := -4^7 + 9^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 8^3$	$49727 := -4^8 - 9^0 - 7^4 + 2^4 + 7^6$
$49362 := -4^6 + 9^4 + 3^5 + 6^6 - 2^1$	$49563 := -4^1 + 9^3 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 3^7$	$49728 := 4^2 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 2^7 + 8^5$
$49363 := -4^6 - 9^0 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 3^8$	$49584 := -4^7 - 9^2 + 5^0 + 8^3 + 4^8$	$49742 := -4^7 - 9^1 + 7^3 + 4^8 + 2^8$
$49364 := 4^4 + 9^1 + 3^7 + 6^6 + 4^4$	$49587 := -4^1 - 9^1 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 7^5$	$49745 := -4^7 - 9^2 + 7^2 + 4^8 + 5^4$
$49364 := -4^7 - 9^0 - 3^1 + 6^3 + 4^8$	$49606 := -4^6 - 9^3 + 6^5 - 0^0 + 6^6$	$49761 := -4^4 + 9^5 - 7^5 + 6^5 - 1^0$
$49365 := -4^1 + 9^5 - 3^8 + 6^1 - 5^5$	$49625 := -4^5 + 9^5 - 6^5 + 2^0 - 5^4$	$49762 := -4^2 + 9^3 + 7^4 + 6^6 - 2^3$
$49368 := 4^1 + 9^1 + 3^7 + 6^6 + 8^3$	$49632 := -4^1 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 2^6$	$49763 := -4^4 + 9^5 - 7^5 + 6^5 + 3^0$
$49385 := 4^7 + 9^2 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 5^3$	$49635 := -4^3 - 9^0 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 5^5$	$49765 := -4^2 + 9^0 - 7^0 + 6^6 + 5^5$
$49386 := 4^7 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 6^3$	$49637 := 4^2 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 7^2$	$49765 := -4^2 - 9^0 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 5^5$
$49418 := 4^4 + 9^1 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 8^5$	$49638 := -4^5 - 9^1 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 8^4$	$49768 := -4^4 - 9^3 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 8^4$
$49434 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 4^8$	$49645 := -4^4 - 9^1 - 6^0 + 4^8 - 5^6$	$49769 := -4^2 - 9^0 + 7^4 + 6^6 + 9^3$
$49436 := 4^4 + 9^2 + 4^4 + 3^7 + 6^6$	$49646 := -4^5 - 9^2 - 6^0 + 4^6 + 6^6$	$49784 := 4^3 + 9^2 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 4^3$
		$49785 := 4^1 + 9^2 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 5^3$
		$49786 := -4^1 - 9^0 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 6^3$
		$49788 := -4^1 + 9^3 + 7^5 + 8^5 - 8^3$

$49834 := -4^5 + 9^5 - 8^4 + 3^0 - 4^6$	$49898 := 4^7 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 9^3 + 8^5$	$50628 := -5^3 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 2^1 + 8^4$
$49835 := -4^2 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 5^6$	$49899 := 4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^1 + 9^3$	$50633 := -5^6 + 0^1 + 6^6 - 3^4 + 3^9$
$49836 := 4^4 + 9^3 + 8^1 + 3^7 + 6^6$	$49925 := -4^3 + 9^4 + 9^5 + 2^2 - 5^6$	$50634 := -5^6 + 0^1 - 6^1 + 3^6 + 4^8$
$49836 := -4^5 + 9^2 + 8^4 + 3^3 + 6^6$	$49944 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 9^3 + 4^3 + 4^8$	$50635 := 5^3 + 0^1 + 6^6 + 3^6 + 5^5$
$49837 := -4^8 - 9^2 - 8^1 - 3^7 + 7^6$	$49963 := -4^7 - 9^0 + 9^1 + 6^6 + 3^9$	$50639 := -5^4 + 0^1 - 6^5 - 3^2 + 9^5$
$49845 := -4^3 - 9^0 - 8^0 + 4^8 - 5^6$	$49968 := -4^3 + 9^1 - 9^3 + 6^6 + 8^4$	$50642 := -5^3 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 4^6 + 2^4$
$49846 := -4^7 + 9^3 + 8^0 + 4^8 - 6^2$	$49968 := 4^7 + 9^2 + 9^3 + 6^1 + 8^5$	$50644 := -5^3 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 4^6$
$49854 := -4^1 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 5^4 + 4^7$	$49985 := -4^3 + 9^4 + 9^5 + 8^2 - 5^6$	$50649 := -5^4 + 0^1 - 6^5 + 4^0 + 9^5$
$49856 := -4^9 - 9^3 + 8^5 + 5^2 + 6^7$	$49987 := 4^6 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 7^0$	$50664 := -5^3 + 0^0 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 4^6$
$49857 := 4^4 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$50247 := -5^6 + 0^0 - 2^3 + 4^8 + 7^3$	$50678 := -5^2 + 0^1 + 6^6 - 7^2 + 8^4$
$49858 := -4^5 + 9^5 - 8^4 + 5^2 - 8^4$	$50249 := -5^6 + 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^8 + 9^2$	$50682 := -5^1 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 8^4 - 2^6$
$49859 := -4^2 - 9^4 + 8^3 - 5^5 + 9^5$	$50336 := -5^5 + 0^0 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 6^6$	$50684 := -5^1 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 8^4 - 4^3$
$49859 := 4^7 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 5^4 + 9^2$	$50342 := -5^6 + 0^1 - 3^4 + 4^8 + 2^9$	$50697 := -5^4 + 0^1 - 6^5 + 9^5 + 7^2$
$49872 := 4^4 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 7^5 + 2^5$	$50354 := -5^7 - 0^0 - 3^0 + 5^8 - 4^9$	$50745 := -5^6 + 0^1 - 7^6 + 4^9 - 5^7$
$49874 := -4^7 + 9^3 - 8^1 + 7^0 + 4^8$	$50358 := -5^7 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 5^8 - 8^6$	$50746 := -5^1 + 0^1 - 7^0 + 4^6 + 6^6$
$49876 := 4^1 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 7^5 + 6^3$	$50367 := 5^5 + 0^1 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 7^3$	$50763 := -5^6 + 0^1 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 3^9$
$49880 := -4^7 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 8^5 - 0^0$	$50421 := -5^6 - 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^9 - 1^0$	$50764 := 5^1 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 4^6$
$49882 := -4^7 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 2^0$	$50422 := -5^6 - 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^8 + 2^8$	$50827 := 5^6 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 7^4$
$49883 := 4^7 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 8^5 + 3^6$	$50423 := -5^6 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^9 - 3^0$	$50867 := -5^1 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 7^5$
$49885 := -4^7 + 9^5 - 8^0 + 8^4 + 5^5$	$50424 := -5^6 + 0^0 + 4^4 + 2^8 + 4^8$	$50876 := 5^1 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^5 + 6^4$
$49890 := 4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 0^1$	$50425 := -5^6 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^9 + 5^0$	$50886 := 5^3 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 8^4 + 6^6$
$49891 := 4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 1^0$	$50428 := -5^6 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^2 + 8^3$	$50935 := 5^6 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 5^6$
$49892 := 4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 2^1$	$50432 := -5^6 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 2^9$	$50944 := -5^6 + 0^1 + 9^1 + 4^5 + 4^8$
$49893 := 4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 3^1$	$50472 := -5^6 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 7^2 + 2^9$	$51269 := -5^1 - 1^0 + 2^1 - 6^5 + 9^5$
$49894 := 4^1 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 4^7$	$50488 := -5^6 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 8^2 + 8^3$	$51448 := -5^6 + 1^0 + 4^5 + 4^8 + 8^3$
$49895 := -4^7 + 9^1 + 8^4 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$50534 := -5^6 - 0^0 + 5^4 - 3^0 + 4^8$	$51462 := -5^6 - 1^0 + 4^8 + 6^4 + 2^8$
$49895 := 4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 5^1$	$50536 := 5^2 + 0^0 + 5^5 + 3^6 + 6^6$	$51464 := -5^6 + 1^0 + 4^4 + 6^4 + 4^8$
$49896 := 4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 6^1$	$50548 := -5^6 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 8^3$	$51738 := -5^2 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 3^7 + 8^5$
$49897 := 4^7 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 7^1$	$50624 := -5^3 - 0^0 + 6^6 - 2^1 + 4^6$	$51823 := -5^4 - 1^0 + 8^5 - 2^1 + 3^9$
		$51829 := -5^5 - 1^0 - 8^4 + 2^1 + 9^5$
		$51843 := -5^4 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 3^9$
		$51863 := -5^4 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^9$

$51954 := -5^5 + 1^0 + 9^5 + 5^3 - 4^6$	$52396 := -5^3 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 9^5 + 6^0$	$52609 := -5^4 + 2^4 + 6^6 + 0^0 + 9^4$
$51992 := -5^4 + 1^0 - 9^4 + 9^5 + 2^7$	$52398 := -5^2 - 2^0 - 3^8 + 9^5 - 8^2$	$52623 := -5^4 - 2^0 + 6^6 + 2^5 + 3^8$
$51996 := -5^1 - 1^0 + 9^3 + 9^5 - 6^5$	$52434 := -5^2 + 2^3 + 4^7 + 3^9 + 4^7$	$52632 := -5^4 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 2^5$
$52034 := -5^6 - 2^6 + 0^1 + 3^7 + 4^8$	$52437 := -5^6 - 2^2 + 4^8 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$52633 := -5^4 + 2^5 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 3^8$
$52083 := -5^4 + 2^8 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$52438 := -5^1 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 3^9 + 8^5$	$52636 := -5^4 + 2^3 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 6^6$
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$52239 := -5^2 - 2^8 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 9^5$	$52457 := -5^2 - 2^8 - 4^8 + 5^4 + 7^6$	$52638 := -5^2 - 2^2 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 8^5$
$52247 := -5^6 - 2^0 - 2^6 + 4^8 + 7^4$	$52463 := -5^4 - 2^7 - 4^0 + 6^6 + 3^8$	$52639 := -5^4 + 2^7 + 6^6 + 3^8 - 9^2$
$52295 := -5^5 + 2^3 - 2^9 + 9^5 - 5^5$	$52472 := -5^2 + 2^7 - 4^8 + 7^6 + 2^8$	$52653 := -5^4 - 2^6 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 3^8$
$52299 := -5^3 - 2^5 - 2^5 - 9^4 + 9^5$	$52473 := -5^3 + 2^9 - 4^8 + 7^6 - 3^3$	$52659 := -5^5 + 2^6 + 6^6 + 5^6 - 9^4$
$52328 := -5^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 2^0 + 8^5$	$52475 := -5^2 + 2^9 - 4^8 + 7^6 - 5^3$	$52673 := -5^2 - 2^9 + 6^6 - 7^1 + 3^8$
$52329 := -5^3 - 2^1 - 3^8 - 2^5 + 9^5$	$52476 := -5^6 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 7^4 + 6^2$	$52679 := -5^2 - 2^9 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 9^4$
$52343 := -5^6 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^8 + 3^7$	$52485 := -5^1 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 5^6$	$52683 := -5^2 + 2^8 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 3^9$
$52344 := -5^6 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^6 + 4^8$	$52493 := -5^5 - 2^6 - 4^6 + 9^5 + 3^6$	$52692 := -5^1 - 2^3 + 6^6 + 9^4 - 2^9$
$52346 := -5^4 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^6$	$52496 := -5^4 - 2^5 - 4^3 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$52693 := -5^2 - 2^8 + 6^6 + 9^4 - 3^5$
$52347 := -5^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^8 + 7^6$	$52497 := -5^5 - 2^1 - 4^5 + 9^5 - 7^4$	$52695 := -5^1 - 2^9 + 6^6 + 9^4 - 5^1$
$52363 := -5^4 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 6^6 + 3^8$	$52498 := 5^6 + 2^3 + 4^6 + 9^0 + 8^5$	$52698 := -5^1 - 2^1 + 6^6 + 9^4 - 8^3$
$52368 := -5^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 + 8^5$	$52499 := -5^1 + 2^5 - 4^2 + 9^5 - 9^4$	$52699 := -5^1 - 2^9 + 6^6 - 9^0 + 9^4$
$52372 := 5^6 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 7^5 + 2^8$	$52524 := -5^6 - 2^8 + 5^5 - 2^8 + 4^8$	$52708 := 5^5 + 2^3 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 8^5$
$52381 := -5^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 8^5 - 1^0$	$52536 := -5^6 - 2^0 + 5^7 - 3^7 - 6^5$	$52726 := 5^5 + 2^5 + 7^4 + 2^9 + 6^6$
$52382 := -5^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 8^5 - 2^5$	$52548 := -5^1 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 4^6 + 8^5$	$52743 := -5^6 + 2^9 + 7^4 + 4^8 - 3^4$
$52383 := -5^1 - 2^6 + 3^0 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$52549 := -5^6 - 2^7 + 5^7 - 4^7 + 9^4$	$52744 := -5^6 - 2^7 + 7^6 + 4^7 - 4^8$
$52384 := -5^1 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 8^5 - 4^3$	$52563 := -5^2 - 2^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 + 3^8$	$52746 := -5^5 + 2^9 - 7^4 + 4^8 - 6^5$
$52385 := -5^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 8^5 - 5^3$	$52564 := -5^6 - 2^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 4^8$	$52748 := 5^5 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 4^2 + 8^5$
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$52387 := -5^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 8^5 - 7^1$	$52583 := 5^1 + 2^1 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$52768 := 5^5 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 6^2 + 8^5$
$52388 := -5^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 8^5$	$52583 := -5^2 + 2^5 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$52769 := -5^4 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^4$
$52389 := -5^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 8^5 - 9^0$	$52587 := -5^4 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 7^5$	$52783 := 5^5 + 2^1 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 3^4$
$52394 := -5^3 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 9^5 - 4^0$	$52596 := -5^4 - 2^0 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$52784 := -5^2 - 2^4 - 7^5 + 8^4 + 4^8$
		$52789 := 5^5 + 2^3 + 7^5 + 8^5 + 9^2$
		$52793 := -5^5 - 2^0 - 7^4 + 9^5 - 3^6$
		$52832 := 5^3 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 2^7$

$52833 := 5^3 + 2^8 + 8^5 + 3^0 + 3^9$	$53093 := -5^3 + 3^6 + 0^0 + 9^5 - 3^8$	$53426 := -5^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 2^9 + 6^6$
$52834 := 5^3 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 4^4$	$53096 := -5^3 + 3^1 + 0^0 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$53436 := -5^2 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 3^8 + 6^6$
$52834 := -5^3 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 3^9 - 4^1$	$53193 := -5^2 + 3^6 + 1^0 + 9^5 - 3^8$	$53464 := -5^1 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^6 + 4^4$
$52836 := -5^3 + 2^8 - 8^3 + 3^8 + 6^6$	$53196 := -5^2 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$53467 := -5^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^6 - 7^0$
$52837 := -5^3 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 3^9 - 7^0$	$53226 := 5^1 + 3^8 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 6^6$	$53468 := -5^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^6 + 8^3$
$52837 := 5^5 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 7^5$	$53226 := -5^1 + 3^8 - 2^1 + 2^4 + 6^6$	$53469 := -5^1 + 3^0 + 4^4 + 6^6 + 9^4$
$52839 := -5^3 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 9^0$	$53229 := -5^5 - 3^7 + 2^2 - 2^9 + 9^5$	$53469 := 5^1 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 6^6 + 9^4$
$52857 := 5^3 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 5^5 + 7^5$	$53245 := -5^6 + 3^4 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 5^5$	$53480 := 5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 0^1$
$52859 := -5^5 - 2^2 + 8^2 - 5^5 + 9^5$	$53246 := 5^1 + 3^8 + 2^3 + 4^2 + 6^6$	$53481 := 5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 1^0$
$52874 := -5^6 + 2^1 - 8^5 + 7^6 - 4^7$	$53249 := -5^6 - 3^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 9^5$	$53482 := 5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 2^1$
$52877 := 5^5 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 7^5$	$53262 := 5^1 + 3^8 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 2^5$	$53482 := -5^2 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 2^5$
$52895 := -5^5 + 2^5 + 8^2 + 9^5 - 5^5$	$53263 := 5^1 + 3^2 + 2^5 + 6^6 + 3^8$	$53483 := 5^1 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 3^9$
$52925 := -5^5 - 2^1 + 9^5 + 2^7 - 5^5$	$53264 := -5^2 + 3^8 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 4^3$	$53484 := 5^1 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 4^5$
$52944 := -5^7 - 2^1 - 9^0 + 4^8 + 4^8$	$53266 := 5^1 + 3^8 + 2^3 + 6^2 + 6^6$	$53485 := 5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 5^1$
$52947 := -5^5 - 2^9 + 9^5 - 4^3 - 7^4$	$53268 := -5^1 + 3^8 - 2^3 + 6^6 + 8^2$	$53486 := 5^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 6^6$
$52954 := -5^6 - 2^0 - 9^2 + 5^5 + 4^8$	$53269 := -5^2 + 3^4 - 2^2 + 6^6 + 9^4$	$53486 := -5^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 8^5 + 6^4$
$52962 := -5^3 - 2^1 + 9^4 + 6^6 - 2^7$	$53279 := -5^5 - 3^5 - 2^0 - 7^4 + 9^5$	$53487 := 5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 7^1$
$52963 := -5^2 - 2^8 + 9^4 + 6^6 + 3^3$	$53283 := -5^2 + 3^6 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$53488 := 5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^1 + 8^5$
$52964 := -5^1 + 2^3 + 9^4 + 6^6 - 4^4$	$53289 := -5^5 - 3^7 + 2^6 - 8^3 + 9^5$	$53489 := 5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 9^1$
$52965 := -5^3 - 2^1 + 9^4 + 6^6 - 5^3$	$53336 := -5^3 + 3^0 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 6^6$	$53489 := -5^5 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 8^1 + 9^5$
$52967 := -5^4 + 2^5 + 9^4 + 6^6 + 7^3$	$53346 := 5^3 + 3^1 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 6^6$	$53493 := -5^5 - 3^5 - 4^0 + 9^5 - 3^7$
$52968 := -5^4 - 2^6 + 9^5 - 6^4 - 8^4$	$53355 := -5^6 - 3^4 + 3^8 - 5^6 + 5^7$	$53497 := -5^5 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 9^5 - 7^4$
$52983 := -5^2 + 2^3 + 9^5 + 8^3 - 3^8$	$53356 := 5^1 + 3^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^6$	$53529 := -5^5 + 3^6 - 5^5 + 2^0 + 9^5$
$52994 := -5^1 + 2^9 - 9^4 + 9^5 - 4^0$	$53376 := 5^3 + 3^3 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 6^6$	$53536 := -5^6 - 3^7 + 5^7 - 3^8 - 6^3$
$52996 := -5^1 + 2^9 - 9^4 + 9^5 + 6^0$	$53396 := 5^3 + 3^3 + 3^3 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$53537 := -5^6 - 3^0 + 5^7 - 3^8 - 7^4$
$53045 := -5^6 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 5^5$	$53396 := -5^6 + 3^2 + 3^7 + 9^5 + 6^5$	$53574 := -5^5 - 3^8 + 5^3 - 7^4 + 4^8$
$53064 := 5^3 + 3^7 + 0^1 + 6^6 + 4^6$	$53397 := -5^5 + 3^1 - 3^7 + 9^5 - 7^3$	$53592 := -5^5 + 3^6 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^6$
$53078 := 5^4 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 8^5$	$53398 := -5^2 + 3^5 + 3^9 + 9^3 + 8^5$	$53594 := -5^1 - 3^6 - 5^4 + 9^5 - 4^6$
$53088 := 5^3 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 8^3 + 8^5$	$53406 := 5^3 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 0^1 + 6^6$	$53596 := -5^6 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 6^5$

$53624 := -5^4 + 3^8 + 6^6 + 2^3 + 4^5$	$53862 := 5^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 6^6 + 2^7$	$54329 := -5^3 - 4^6 - 3^5 - 2^8 + 9^5$
$53627 := -5^6 + 3^9 + 6^6 + 2^9 + 7^4$	$53863 := 5^3 + 3^2 + 8^3 + 6^6 + 3^8$	$54342 := -5^2 - 4^6 - 3^8 + 4^8 - 2^9$
$53628 := 5^4 + 3^7 + 6^6 + 2^6 + 8^4$	$53869 := -5^4 - 3^5 - 8^4 - 6^3 + 9^5$	$54344 := -5^6 + 4^4 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 4^8$
$53643 := -5^2 + 3^6 + 6^6 + 4^6 + 3^7$	$53886 := 5^5 + 3^0 + 8^1 + 8^4 + 6^6$	$54345 := -5^1 - 4^6 - 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^7$
$53647 := 5^3 + 3^8 + 6^6 + 4^4 + 7^2$	$53934 := -5^5 - 3^4 + 9^5 + 3^7 - 4^6$	$54347 := -5^6 + 4^6 - 3^1 + 4^8 + 7^3$
$53648 := -5^2 + 3^2 - 6^5 + 4^8 - 8^4$	$53956 := 5^1 + 3^6 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 6^6$	$54349 := -5^6 + 4^3 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 9^4$
$53649 := -5^1 - 3^1 - 6^4 - 4^6 + 9^5$	$53973 := -5^5 - 3^7 + 9^5 - 7^1 + 3^5$	$54363 := 5^5 + 4^6 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 3^5$
$53649 := 5^3 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$53992 := -5^5 - 3^7 - 9^0 + 9^5 + 2^8$	$54366 := -5^1 - 4^3 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 6^6$
$53662 := -5^2 - 3^6 + 6^5 + 6^6 - 2^4$	$53994 := -5^5 - 3^7 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 4^4$	$54367 := 5^3 + 4^5 + 3^8 + 6^6 + 7^0$
$53664 := -5^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 4^4$	$54008 := -5^6 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 0^1 + 8^4$	$54369 := 5^3 + 4^5 + 3^1 + 6^6 + 9^4$
$53668 := -5^2 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 8^3$	$54024 := -5^6 + 4^6 + 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^8$	$54369 := -5^3 - 4^6 - 3^5 - 6^3 + 9^5$
$53669 := -5^2 - 3^2 + 6^5 + 6^6 - 9^3$	$54034 := -5^6 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 4^8$	$54385 := -5^2 - 4^6 - 3^9 + 8^2 + 5^7$
$53674 := -5^4 + 3^7 - 6^0 + 7^6 - 4^8$	$54089 := -5^6 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 9^2$	$54387 := -5^4 + 4^8 + 3^7 + 8^4 - 7^5$
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$53686 := -5^2 - 3^6 + 6^5 + 8^1 + 6^6$	$54234 := -5^6 + 4^6 - 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^8$	$54451 := -5^7 + 4^6 - 4^9 + 5^8 - 1^0$
$53729 := -5^5 - 3^7 - 7^1 - 2^0 + 9^5$	$54239 := -5^4 - 4^6 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 9^5$	$54453 := -5^7 + 4^6 - 4^9 + 5^8 + 3^0$
$53739 := -5^5 - 3^3 - 7^4 + 3^5 + 9^5$	$54253 := -5^3 - 4^6 + 2^5 + 5^7 - 3^9$	$54459 := -5^3 - 4^6 + 4^4 - 5^4 + 9^5$
$53753 := -5^6 - 3^7 + 7^0 + 5^7 - 3^8$	$54259 := -5^1 - 4^6 - 2^6 - 5^4 + 9^5$	$54475 := -5^6 + 4^6 + 4^8 + 7^3 + 5^3$
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$53843 := 5^3 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 3^9$	$54327 := -5^1 - 4^8 + 3^7 + 2^5 + 7^6$	$54561 := -5^5 + 4^8 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 1^0$
		$54563 := -5^5 + 4^8 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 3^0$
		$54565 := -5^2 - 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 5^7$
		$54566 := 5^1 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 6^6$

$54566 := -5^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 6^6$	$54693 := -5^3 - 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^5 + 3^4$	$54902 := -5^5 - 4^5 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 2^0$
$54569 := -5^3 - 4^7 + 5^7 - 6^5 + 9^3$	$54696 := -5^1 - 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^5 - 6^3$	$54903 := -5^5 - 4^5 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 3^1$
$54584 := -5^5 - 4^6 + 5^7 + 8^2 - 4^7$	$54698 := -5^1 - 4^4 + 6^1 + 9^5 - 8^4$	$54904 := -5^5 + 4^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 - 4^5$
$54628 := -5^5 + 4^8 - 6^5 + 2^0 - 8^1$	$54704 := -5^8 + 4^8 + 7^6 + 0^1 + 4^9$	$54905 := -5^5 - 4^5 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 5^1$
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$54632 := 5^5 + 4^6 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 2^9$	$54743 := -5^6 + 4^6 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 3^6$	$54907 := -5^5 - 4^5 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 7^1$
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$54642 := -5^5 - 4^0 - 6^5 + 4^8 + 2^3$	$54839 := -5^2 - 4^6 - 8^1 - 3^4 + 9^5$	$54926 := -5^1 - 4^6 + 9^5 - 2^4 - 6^1$
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$54655 := -5^1 - 4^3 - 6^5 - 5^6 + 5^7$	$54859 := 5^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 5^6 + 5^6$	$54929 := -5^2 - 4^6 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 9^5$
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$54662 := -5^2 - 4^0 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 2^8$	$54892 := -5^1 - 4^3 - 8^4 + 9^5 + 2^3$	$54938 := -5^1 - 4^0 + 9^5 - 3^2 - 8^4$
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$54692 := -5^5 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^5 + 2^7$	$54900 := -5^5 - 4^5 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 0^0$	$54952 := -5^1 - 4^6 + 9^5 + 5^1 - 2^0$
	$54901 := -5^5 - 4^5 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 1^0$	$54954 := -5^1 + 4^0 + 9^5 + 5^1 - 4^6$
		$54962 := -5^1 - 4^6 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 2^3$
		$54963 := -5^1 - 4^6 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 3^2$

$54965 := -5^2 - 4^6 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 5^0$	$55314 := -5^5 + 5^7 - 3^9 + 1^0 - 4^1$	$55468 := -5^1 + 5^4 + 4^6 + 6^6 + 8^4$
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$54968 := -5^1 - 4^2 + 9^5 + 6^2 - 8^4$	$55317 := -5^5 + 5^7 - 3^9 + 1^0 - 7^0$	$55483 := 5^5 + 5^5 + 4^7 + 8^5 + 3^4$
$54976 := -5^2 - 4^6 + 9^5 + 7^2 - 6^0$	$55319 := -5^5 + 5^7 - 3^9 + 1^0 + 9^0$	$55579 := -5^5 - 5^0 - 5^0 - 7^3 + 9^5$
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		$55843 := 5^1 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 3^8$
		$55843 := -5^5 + 5^0 - 8^1 + 4^8 - 3^8$

$55847 := -5^3 - 5^7 + 8^2 + 4^7 + 7^6$	$55918 := -5^5 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 1^0 - 8^1$	$55946 := -5^5 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 6^0$
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$55879 := -5^7 + 5^6 + 8^0 + 7^6 + 9^3$	$55919 := -5^1 - 5^5 - 9^0 + 1^0 + 9^5$	$55948 := -5^6 + 5^7 - 9^4 + 4^0 + 8^1$
$55883 := -5^6 + 5^7 - 8^2 + 8^1 - 3^8$	$55920 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 0^1$	$55949 := -5^5 + 5^2 - 9^0 + 4^0 + 9^5$
$55889 := -5^3 + 5^7 - 8^5 + 8^4 + 9^4$	$55921 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 1^0$	$55950 := -5^5 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 0^1$
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$55892 := -5^2 - 5^5 + 8^0 + 9^5 - 2^3$	$55923 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 3^1$	$55952 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 2^5$
$55893 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 8^0 + 9^5 - 3^3$	$55924 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 4^1$	$55953 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 3^2$
$55894 := -5^2 - 5^5 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 4^1$	$55925 := -5^1 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 2^0 - 5^5$	$55954 := -5^5 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 4^1$
$55895 := -5^1 - 5^2 + 8^0 + 9^5 - 5^5$	$55926 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 6^1$	$55955 := -5^5 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 5^2$
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$55907 := -5^2 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 7^1$	$55937 := -5^1 - 5^4 + 9^5 - 3^4 - 7^4$	$55967 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 6^0 + 7^2$
$55908 := -5^2 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 8^1$	$55938 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 3^3 - 8^1$	$55969 := -5^5 + 5^3 - 9^2 + 6^0 + 9^5$
$55909 := -5^1 - 5^5 - 9^1 - 0^0 + 9^5$	$55939 := -5^5 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 3^2 + 9^5$	$55971 := -5^5 - 5^0 + 9^5 + 7^2 - 1^0$
$55912 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 1^0 - 2^3$	$55940 := -5^5 - 5^0 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 0^0$	$55972 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 2^2$
$55913 := -5^5 - 5^0 + 9^5 - 1^0 - 3^2$	$55941 := -5^6 + 5^7 - 9^4 + 4^0 + 1^0$	$55973 := -5^2 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 7^1 + 3^4$
$55914 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 1^0 - 4^1$	$55942 := -5^5 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 2^4$	$55974 := -5^5 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 7^2 - 4^1$
$55915 := -5^1 - 5^1 + 9^5 + 1^0 - 5^5$	$55943 := -5^6 + 5^7 - 9^4 + 4^0 + 3^1$	$55975 := -5^2 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 7^2 + 5^3$
$55916 := -5^5 - 5^0 + 9^5 - 1^0 - 6^1$	$55944 := -5^5 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 4^2 - 4^0$	$55976 := -5^6 + 5^7 - 9^4 + 7^0 + 6^2$
$55917 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 1^0 - 7^0$	$55945 := -5^1 + 5^2 + 9^5 + 4^0 - 5^5$	$55977 := -5^5 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 7^2 - 7^0$
		$55979 := -5^2 - 5^5 + 9^2 - 7^0 + 9^5$
		$55982 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 8^0 + 2^6$
		$55984 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 8^0 + 4^3$

$55986 := -5^5 - 5^0 + 9^5 + 8^2 - 6^0$	$56364 := 5^5 + 6^1 + 3^8 + 6^6 + 4^2$	$56546 := -5^4 + 6^2 - 5^4 + 4^8 - 6^5$
$55988 := -5^5 - 5^0 + 9^5 + 8^0 + 8^2$	$56364 := -5^6 - 6^4 - 3^3 + 6^5 + 4^8$	$56549 := -5^5 - 6^0 + 5^4 + 4^0 + 9^5$
$55992 := -5^1 - 5^5 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 2^6$	$56379 := -5^2 - 6^0 - 3^5 - 7^4 + 9^5$	$56563 := 5^1 + 6^3 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 3^8$
$55993 := -5^6 + 5^7 - 9^4 + 9^2 - 3^3$	$56382 := 5^5 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 2^5$	$56564 := -5^2 - 6^4 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 4^8$
$55994 := -5^5 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 4^3$	$56384 := -5^4 + 6^4 + 3^8 + 8^5 + 4^7$	$56594 := -5^4 + 6^4 - 5^5 + 9^5 - 4^0$
$55995 := -5^1 - 5^1 + 9^2 + 9^5 - 5^5$	$56386 := 5^5 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 6^6$	$56596 := -5^4 + 6^0 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 6^4$
$55997 := -5^2 - 5^4 - 9^0 + 9^5 - 7^4$	$56398 := -5^4 - 6^4 - 3^6 + 9^5 - 8^0$	$56597 := -5^2 - 6^0 - 5^2 + 9^5 - 7^4$
$55998 := -5^5 + 5^0 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 8^2$	$56429 := -5^5 - 6^1 - 4^0 + 2^9 + 9^5$	$56624 := -5^4 - 6^5 + 6^0 - 2^9 + 4^8$
$55999 := -5^1 - 5^5 - 9^0 + 9^2 + 9^5$	$56432 := -5^4 + 6^6 + 4^6 + 3^8 - 2^8$	$56632 := 5^1 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 2^3$
$56097 := -5^6 - 6^6 + 0^1 + 9^3 + 7^6$	$56433 := 5^1 + 6^6 + 4^5 + 3^7 + 3^8$	$56633 := 5^1 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 3^7$
$56219 := -5^5 - 6^3 + 2^9 - 1^0 + 9^5$	$56433 := -5^4 - 6^5 + 4^8 + 3^3 - 3^6$	$56634 := 5^5 + 6^2 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 4^4$
$56235 := -5^6 - 6^3 + 2^9 - 3^8 + 5^7$	$56435 := -5^6 - 6^2 + 4^8 + 3^8 - 5^0$	$56634 := -5^6 - 6^4 + 6^5 + 3^5 + 4^8$
$56239 := -5^4 - 6^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 9^5$	$56436 := -5^2 - 6^4 + 4^8 - 3^1 - 6^5$	$56637 := -5^6 - 6^6 + 6^4 - 3^3 + 7^6$
$56253 := -5^2 + 6^6 - 2^6 + 5^5 + 3^8$	$56437 := -5^6 - 6^2 + 4^8 + 3^8 + 7^0$	$56639 := 5^5 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 3^4 + 9^4$
$56254 := -5^4 - 6^5 - 2^8 - 5^4 + 4^8$	$56439 := -5^5 + 6^4 - 4^5 + 3^5 + 9^5$	$56672 := -5^6 + 6^4 - 6^6 + 7^6 + 2^3$
$56258 := 5^2 + 6^5 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 8^5$	$56439 := 5^5 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 3^4 + 9^4$	$56673 := 5^1 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^7$
$56269 := -5^5 + 6^0 + 2^7 + 6^3 + 9^5$	$56459 := -5^2 + 6^6 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 9^4$	$56673 := -5^6 + 6^4 - 6^6 + 7^6 + 3^2$
$56273 := -5^4 + 6^6 - 2^2 + 7^5 - 3^8$	$56460 := -5^1 - 6^4 + 4^8 - 6^5 + 0^0$	$56682 := 5^6 + 6^0 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 2^9$
$56274 := -5^5 + 6^6 + 2^5 + 7^5 - 4^6$	$56473 := -5^6 - 6^1 + 4^8 + 7^1 + 3^8$	$56689 := -5^4 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 8^4 + 9^4$
$56279 := -5^2 - 6^3 - 2^7 - 7^4 + 9^5$	$56479 := -5^5 + 6^3 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^5$	$56694 := -5^4 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 9^4 + 4^6$
$56298 := 5^6 + 6^5 + 2^7 + 9^0 + 8^5$	$56492 := -5^6 + 6^2 + 4^8 + 9^4 - 2^4$	$56696 := -5^4 - 6^3 - 6^3 + 9^5 - 6^4$
$56325 := -5^2 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 2^3 + 5^5$	$56493 := -5^6 - 6^1 + 4^8 + 9^4 + 3^3$	$56728 := -5^4 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 2^1 + 8^5$
$56329 := -5^4 - 6^2 - 3^7 + 2^7 + 9^5$	$56494 := -5^6 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 9^4 + 4^8$	$56743 := -5^1 + 6^5 - 7^5 + 4^8 + 3^5$
$56342 := -5^4 - 6^5 - 3^6 + 4^8 - 2^6$	$56496 := -5^2 - 6^4 + 4^3 + 9^5 - 6^4$	$56749 := -5^4 - 6^5 + 7^3 + 4^8 - 9^3$
$56344 := -5^5 + 6^3 - 3^7 + 4^8 - 4^6$	$56499 := -5^6 + 6^2 + 4^8 + 9^4 - 9^1$	$56749 := 5^5 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$56344 := 5^5 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 4^0$	$56523 := -5^4 - 6^4 + 5^7 + 2^1 - 3^9$	$56754 := -5^5 + 6^6 - 7^4 + 5^6 - 4^0$
$56347 := -5^3 + 6^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$56529 := -5^5 - 6^2 + 5^4 + 2^4 + 9^5$	$56756 := -5^5 + 6^0 - 7^4 + 5^6 + 6^6$
$56347 := 5^5 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^0$	$56539 := -5^5 - 6^0 + 5^4 - 3^2 + 9^5$	$56764 := -5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 + 6^6 - 4^3$
$56349 := 5^5 + 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$56542 := -5^4 - 6^5 - 5^4 + 4^8 + 2^5$	$56784 := -5^4 - 6^5 - 7^3 - 8^1 + 4^8$
		$56789 := -5^4 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 8^3 - 9^4$
		$56804 := -5^3 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 4^7$
		$56839 := -5^2 - 6^1 + 8^1 - 3^7 + 9^5$

$56852 := -5^6 - 6^4 - 8^4 + 5^7 - 2^8$	$57335 := -5^7 + 7^6 - 3^0 + 3^7 + 5^6$	$57642 := -5^1 - 7^2 - 6^5 + 4^8 - 2^6$
$56858 := 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 + 5^6 + 8^5$	$57352 := -5^7 + 7^6 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 2^4$	$57643 := -5^3 - 7^0 - 6^5 + 4^8 + 3^2$
$56859 := 5^1 + 6^6 + 8^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$57375 := -5^5 - 7^3 - 3^9 + 7^4 + 5^7$	$57644 := -5^3 - 7^1 - 6^5 + 4^2 + 4^8$
$56859 := -5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 - 5^5 + 9^5$	$57378 := 5^3 + 7^4 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 8^5$	$57646 := -5^6 + 7^5 - 6^4 + 4^8 - 6^5$
$56873 := 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 3^9$	$57379 := -5^1 - 7^4 + 3^6 + 7^1 + 9^5$	$57648 := -5^4 + 7^0 - 6^5 + 4^8 + 8^3$
$56893 := -5^4 - 6^4 + 8^1 + 9^5 - 3^5$	$57393 := 5^6 + 7^4 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 3^9$	$57664 := -5^3 - 7^1 + 6^2 - 6^5 + 4^8$
$56894 := -5^4 + 6^1 - 8^3 + 9^5 - 4^5$	$57394 := -5^4 - 7^1 + 3^0 + 9^5 - 4^5$	$57669 := -5^3 - 7^5 + 6^5 + 6^5 + 9^5$
$56899 := 5^6 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 9^0 + 9^3$	$57396 := -5^1 - 7^3 - 3^2 + 9^5 - 6^4$	$57684 := -5^1 - 7^1 - 6^5 - 8^2 + 4^8$
$56941 := -5^5 - 6^1 + 9^5 + 4^5 - 1^0$	$57398 := -5^1 - 7^4 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 8^3$	$57688 := -5^6 + 7^0 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 8^5$
$56942 := -5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 + 4^8 - 2^6$	$57399 := -5^1 - 7^4 + 3^3 + 9^3 + 9^5$	$57689 := -5^4 - 7^1 - 6^3 - 8^3 + 9^5$
$56943 := -5^5 - 6^1 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 3^0$	$57425 := -5^5 - 7^5 - 4^4 - 2^9 + 5^7$	$57693 := -5^4 - 7^0 - 6^0 + 9^5 - 3^6$
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$56954 := -5^5 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 4^5$	$57538 := -5^4 - 7^3 + 5^7 - 3^9 + 8^2$	$57839 := -5^4 - 7^3 + 8^0 - 3^5 + 9^5$
$56963 := -5^2 - 6^2 + 9^5 - 6^4 - 3^6$	$57539 := -5^3 - 7^2 + 5^7 - 3^9 - 9^3$	$57868 := 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 6^5 + 8^5$
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$56984 := -5^2 + 6^4 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 4^7$	$57596 := -5^2 - 7^1 - 5^3 + 9^5 - 6^4$	$57932 := -5^3 - 7^1 + 9^5 - 3^6 - 2^8$
$56997 := -5^5 + 6^0 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 7^3$	$57606 := 5^5 + 7^2 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 6^6$	$57933 := -5^3 - 7^3 + 9^5 + 3^4 - 3^6$
$56998 := -5^2 - 6^4 - 9^3 + 9^5 - 8^0$	$57624 := -5^3 - 7^1 - 6^5 - 2^2 + 4^8$	$57934 := -5^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 3^3 - 4^5$
$57264 := -5^2 - 7^3 - 2^7 - 6^5 + 4^8$	$57629 := -5^3 - 7^0 - 6^4 + 2^1 + 9^5$	$57936 := -5^1 - 7^3 + 9^5 - 3^6 - 6^2$
$57269 := -5^3 - 7^3 - 2^4 - 6^4 + 9^5$	$57641 := -5^3 + 7^1 - 6^5 + 4^8 - 1^0$	$57938 := -5^4 - 7^0 + 9^5 + 3^3 - 8^3$
		$57939 := -5^4 + 7^0 - 9^3 + 3^5 + 9^5$
		$57952 := -5^3 - 7^3 + 9^5 - 5^4 - 2^2$
		$57953 := -5^2 - 7^3 + 9^5 + 5^0 - 3^6$

$57954 := -5^2 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 5^4 - 4^6$	$58274 := -5^5 - 8^4 + 2^3 - 7^2 + 4^8$	$58354 := -5^2 + 8^0 - 3^9 + 5^7 - 4^3$
$57955 := -5^2 + 7^6 - 9^5 + 5^1 - 5^4$	$58275 := -5^6 - 8^4 - 2^7 - 7^0 + 5^7$	$58364 := -5^4 + 8^1 - 3^8 + 6^1 + 4^8$
$57957 := -5^2 - 7^3 + 9^5 - 5^5 + 7^4$	$58279 := -5^4 - 8^2 - 2^5 - 7^2 + 9^5$	$58365 := -5^4 + 8^3 - 3^9 + 6^2 + 5^7$
$57962 := -5^4 + 7^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 - 2^9$	$58284 := -5^5 - 8^4 - 2^5 + 8^0 + 4^8$	$58369 := -5^4 - 8^2 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 9^5$
$57967 := -5^4 - 7^1 - 9^5 - 6^0 + 7^6$	$58289 := -5^4 - 8^1 - 2^7 + 8^0 + 9^5$	$58382 := -5^4 + 8^5 - 3^8 + 8^5 + 2^5$
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$57972 := -5^4 - 7^0 - 9^5 + 7^6 - 2^1$	$58293 := -5^1 - 8^3 + 2^2 + 9^5 - 3^5$	$58386 := -5^4 + 8^5 - 3^8 + 8^5 + 6^2$
$57973 := -5^1 - 7^3 + 9^5 + 7^0 - 3^6$	$58294 := -5^4 - 8^0 - 2^7 + 9^5 - 4^0$	$58390 := -5^4 - 8^1 - 3^3 + 9^5 + 0^0$
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$57975 := -5^4 - 7^0 - 9^5 + 7^6 + 5^0$	$58296 := -5^4 + 8^0 - 2^7 + 9^5 - 6^0$	$58392 := -5^4 - 8^0 + 3^0 + 9^5 - 2^5$
$57976 := -5^4 + 7^1 - 9^5 + 7^6 - 6^1$	$58296 := -5^4 - 8^0 - 2^7 + 9^5 + 6^0$	$58393 := -5^4 - 8^0 - 3^1 + 9^5 - 3^3$
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$57984 := -5^4 + 7^6 - 9^5 + 8^1 + 4^0$	$58315 := -5^3 - 8^0 - 3^9 - 1^0 + 5^7$	$58397 := -5^4 + 8^0 - 3^3 + 9^5 - 7^0$
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$57993 := -5^4 + 7^6 - 9^5 + 9^1 + 3^2$	$58325 := -5^3 - 8^1 - 3^9 + 2^4 + 5^7$	$58399 := -5^4 + 8^0 - 3^3 + 9^0 + 9^5$
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$57995 := -5^1 - 7^3 - 9^2 + 9^5 - 5^4$	$58335 := -5^2 - 8^0 - 3^4 - 3^9 + 5^7$	$58409 := -5^3 - 8^3 - 4^1 + 0^0 + 9^5$
$57999 := -5^4 - 7^3 - 9^0 - 9^2 + 9^5$	$58339 := -5^4 - 8^0 - 3^1 - 3^4 + 9^5$	$58419 := -5^4 - 8^1 + 4^1 - 1^0 + 9^5$
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$58146 := -5^3 + 8^3 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 6^5$	$58342 := -5^3 - 8^3 - 3^8 + 4^8 + 2^2$	$58434 := -5^2 - 8^3 - 4^1 - 3^8 + 4^8$
$58193 := -5^3 - 8^0 - 1^0 + 9^5 - 3^6$	$58343 := -5^4 - 8^1 + 3^0 + 4^8 - 3^8$	$58435 := -5^1 - 8^0 - 4^0 - 3^9 + 5^7$
$58239 := -5^2 - 8^2 + 2^3 - 3^6 + 9^5$	$58345 := -5^2 - 8^1 - 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^7$	$58437 := -5^2 - 8^3 + 4^8 - 3^8 - 7^0$
$58246 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 2^9 + 4^8 - 6^5$	$58346 := -5^4 - 8^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^6$	$58439 := -5^2 - 8^3 - 4^3 - 3^2 + 9^5$
$58253 := -5^3 + 8^2 - 2^7 + 5^7 - 3^9$	$58347 := -5^5 - 8^4 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 7^2$	$58442 := -5^5 - 8^0 - 4^6 + 4^8 + 2^7$
$58254 := -5^3 - 8^4 + 2^6 - 5^5 + 4^8$	$58348 := -5^4 - 8^0 - 3^8 + 4^8 - 8^0$	$58449 := -5^2 - 8^3 + 4^0 - 4^3 + 9^5$
$58257 := -5^5 - 8^2 + 2^7 + 5^7 - 7^5$	$58349 := -5^3 - 8^3 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 9^5$	$58452 := -5^6 + 8^2 - 4^6 + 5^7 - 2^4$
$58259 := -5^2 - 8^3 - 2^7 - 5^3 + 9^5$	$58352 := -5^2 - 8^0 - 3^9 + 5^7 - 2^6$	$58453 := -5^1 - 8^3 + 4^8 - 5^1 - 3^8$
		$58456 := -5^6 - 8^4 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 6^2$
		$58457 := -5^5 + 8^1 + 4^4 + 5^7 - 7^5$
		$58459 := -5^1 - 8^3 + 4^8 + 5^0 - 9^4$

$58463 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 4^8 - 6^5 + 3^6$	$58563 := 5^4 + 8^4 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 3^8$	$58726 := -5^4 - 8^4 + 7^5 - 2^4 + 6^6$
$58469 := -5^1 - 8^3 - 4^3 + 6^0 + 9^5$	$58563 := -5^5 - 8^3 + 5^6 + 6^6 - 3^4$	$58739 := -5^4 - 8^0 + 7^3 - 3^3 + 9^5$
$58474 := -5^5 - 8^3 - 4^5 - 7^4 + 4^8$	$58565 := -5^6 - 8^4 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 5^7$	$58746 := -5^4 - 8^4 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 6^6$
$58475 := -5^6 + 8^2 - 4^6 + 7^1 + 5^7$	$58569 := -5^1 - 8^3 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 9^5$	$58749 := -5^2 + 8^2 - 7^3 + 4^1 + 9^5$
$58476 := -5^3 - 8^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 6^6$	$58579 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 5^1 + 7^6 - 9^5$	$58763 := -5^5 + 8^5 - 7^5 + 6^6 - 3^6$
$58478 := -5^4 - 8^4 + 4^8 - 7^4 + 8^2$	$58583 := -5^6 - 8^2 + 5^7 - 8^4 + 3^5$	$58769 := -5^4 + 8^0 + 7^3 + 6^0 + 9^5$
$58479 := -5^1 - 8^3 - 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^5$	$58594 := -5^7 - 8^0 - 5^8 + 9^6 - 4^6$	$58789 := -5^3 - 8^2 - 7^1 - 8^2 + 9^5$
$58490 := -5^4 + 8^0 + 4^3 + 9^5 + 0^0$	$58596 := -5^7 - 8^4 - 5^8 + 9^6 + 6^0$	$58793 := -5^1 - 8^0 - 7^1 + 9^5 - 3^5$
$58491 := -5^4 + 8^2 + 4^1 + 9^5 - 1^0$	$58597 := -5^4 - 8^0 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 7^2$	$58794 := -5^1 - 8^0 + 7^1 + 9^5 - 4^4$
$58492 := -5^2 - 8^3 - 4^1 + 9^5 - 2^4$	$58629 := -5^3 - 8^3 + 6^3 + 2^0 + 9^5$	$58796 := -5^3 - 8^0 - 7^3 + 9^5 + 6^3$
$58493 := -5^2 - 8^3 - 4^2 + 9^5 - 3^1$	$58634 := -5^4 - 8^4 + 6^1 - 3^7 + 4^8$	$58829 := -5^3 - 8^2 + 8^0 - 2^5 + 9^5$
$58495 := -5^2 - 8^3 - 4^2 + 9^5 - 5^0$	$58635 := -5^5 - 8^3 + 6^6 - 3^2 + 5^6$	$58834 := -5^3 - 8^1 - 8^1 - 3^8 + 4^8$
$58496 := -5^1 + 8^3 - 4^5 + 9^5 - 6^2$	$58639 := -5^4 + 8^1 - 6^2 + 3^5 + 9^5$	$58835 := -5^6 - 8^4 + 8^3 - 3^4 + 5^7$
$58497 := -5^2 - 8^3 - 4^2 + 9^5 + 7^0$	$58645 := -5^5 - 8^3 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 5^6$	$58839 := -5^1 + 8^2 - 8^3 + 3^5 + 9^5$
$58499 := -5^2 - 8^3 - 4^1 - 9^1 + 9^5$	$58649 := -5^4 + 8^1 + 6^3 + 4^0 + 9^5$	$58843 := -5^3 + 8^0 - 8^1 + 4^8 - 3^8$
$58523 := -5^6 - 8^4 + 5^7 + 2^7 - 3^2$	$58652 := -5^5 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 5^6 - 2^9$	$58852 := -5^6 - 8^2 - 8^4 + 5^7 + 2^9$
$58524 := -5^6 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 2^7 - 4^6$	$58653 := -5^5 - 8^3 + 6^6 + 5^6 + 3^2$	$58855 := -5^5 - 8^1 - 8^3 - 5^6 + 5^7$
$58525 := -5^6 - 8^4 + 5^3 - 2^2 + 5^7$	$58654 := -5^6 - 8^4 - 6^1 + 5^7 + 4^4$	$58869 := -5^3 + 8^1 - 8^2 + 6^0 + 9^5$
$58526 := -5^6 - 8^4 + 5^7 + 2^7 - 6^1$	$58656 := -5^6 - 8^4 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 6^3$	$58873 := -5^6 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 3^8$
$58527 := -5^5 - 8^5 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 7^5$	$58678 := -5^4 - 8^2 + 6^6 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$58879 := -5^4 - 8^1 + 8^3 - 7^2 + 9^5$
$58529 := -5^1 - 8^1 + 5^1 - 2^9 + 9^5$	$58679 := -5^2 - 8^0 - 6^0 - 7^3 + 9^5$	$58892 := -5^2 - 8^2 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 2^2$
$58534 := -5^5 - 8^0 + 5^7 - 3^4 - 4^7$	$58692 := -5^1 - 8^1 - 6^3 + 9^5 - 2^7$	$58893 := -5^2 - 8^2 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 3^1$
$58539 := -5^4 - 8^0 + 5^3 - 3^2 + 9^5$	$58693 := -5^4 + 8^3 - 6^3 + 9^5 - 3^3$	$58894 := -5^2 - 8^2 + 8^1 - 9^4 + 4^8$
$58543 := -5^5 - 8^2 + 5^7 - 4^7 - 3^2$	$58694 := -5^4 + 8^1 + 6^1 + 9^5 + 4^4$	$58895 := -5^2 - 8^2 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 5^0$
$58544 := -5^3 - 8^4 + 5^7 + 4^5 - 4^7$	$58695 := -5^1 - 8^1 - 6^3 + 9^5 - 5^3$	$58897 := -5^2 - 8^2 - 8^2 + 9^5 + 7^0$
$58545 := -5^6 - 8^4 + 5^3 + 4^2 + 5^7$	$58697 := -5^4 + 8^1 + 6^3 + 9^5 + 7^2$	$58899 := -5^3 - 8^1 - 8^1 - 9^1 + 9^5$
$58546 := -5^5 - 8^2 + 5^7 - 4^7 - 6^1$	$58699 := -5^3 - 8^1 - 6^3 - 9^0 + 9^5$	$58908 := -5^3 - 8^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 - 8^1$
$58548 := -5^7 + 8^4 + 5^8 + 4^6 - 8^6$	$58705 := -5^5 + 8^3 - 7^5 + 0^1 + 5^7$	$58913 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 1^0 - 3^2$
$58549 := -5^1 - 8^3 + 5^0 + 4^2 + 9^5$	$58709 := -5^1 + 8^1 - 7^3 + 0^1 + 9^5$	$58914 := -5^3 - 8^1 + 9^5 - 1^0 - 4^0$
		$58916 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 1^0 - 6^1$
		$58917 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 1^0 - 7^1$
		$58918 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 1^0 - 8^1$

$58920 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 2^1 - 0^0$	$58949 := -5^2 + 8^1 - 9^1 + 4^8 - 9^4$	$58982 := -5^1 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 8^0 - 2^6$
$58921 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 2^0 - 1^0$	$58950 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 0^1$	$58983 := -5^3 - 8^1 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 3^1$
$58922 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 2^0 - 2^1$	$58951 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 1^0$	$58984 := -5^1 - 8^2 + 9^5 + 8^1 - 4^1$
$58923 := -5^1 - 8^1 + 9^5 - 2^5 - 3^4$	$58952 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 2^1$	$58985 := -5^3 - 8^1 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 5^1$
$58924 := -5^1 - 8^1 + 9^5 - 2^7 + 4^2$	$58953 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 3^3$	$58986 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 8^0 - 6^2$
$58925 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 2^0 - 5^0$	$58954 := -5^1 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 5^2 - 4^3$	$58987 := -5^1 - 8^2 + 9^5 + 8^1 - 7^0$
$58925 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 5^0$	$58955 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 5^2$	$58988 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 8^0 + 8^2$
$58926 := -5^2 - 8^2 + 9^5 + 2^1 - 6^2$	$58956 := -5^1 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 5^2 + 6^0$	$58989 := -5^1 - 8^2 + 9^0 + 8^1 + 9^5$
$58927 := -5^1 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 2^2 - 7^2$	$58957 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 7^1$	$58990 := -5^1 - 8^2 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 0^0$
$58928 := -5^2 - 8^2 + 9^5 + 2^5 - 8^2$	$58958 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 5^0 - 8^2$	$58992 := -5^2 + 8^0 - 9^0 + 9^5 - 2^5$
$58929 := -5^2 - 8^2 + 9^0 - 2^5 + 9^5$	$58959 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 5^2 + 9^5$	$58992 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 9^0 + 9^5 - 2^5$
$58931 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 3^2 - 1^0$	$58960 := -5^2 - 8^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 - 0^0$	$58996 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 9^1 + 9^5 - 6^2$
$58932 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 3^3 - 2^6$	$58960 := -5^2 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 6^0 + 0^0$	$58997 := -5^1 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 9^5 - 7^2$
$58933 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 3^2 - 3^4$	$58962 := -5^2 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 6^0 - 2^6$	$58998 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 8^2$
$58934 := -5^2 - 8^1 + 9^5 - 3^4 - 4^0$	$58963 := -5^1 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 6^0 - 3^4$	$59012 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 1^0 - 2^5$
$58935 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 5^0$	$58964 := -5^2 + 8^1 - 9^4 + 6^1 + 4^8$	$59017 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 1^0 - 7^1$
$58936 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 3^4 - 6^1$	$58965 := -5^2 - 8^2 + 9^5 + 6^1 - 5^0$	$59018 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 1^0 - 8^1$
$58938 := -5^4 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 8^3$	$58966 := -5^4 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 6^2 - 6^1$	$59022 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 2^0 - 2^1$
$58939 := -5^2 - 8^0 - 9^2 - 3^1 + 9^5$	$58967 := -5^1 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 6^1 - 7^1$	$59023 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 2^0 - 3^0$
$58940 := -5^3 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 4^2 - 0^0$	$58969 := -5^3 + 8^1 + 9^0 + 6^2 + 9^5$	$59024 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 2^1 - 4^0$
$58940 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 0^0$	$58971 := -5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 + 7^2 - 1^0$	$59025 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 2^0 - 5^0$
$58941 := -5^2 - 8^1 - 9^4 + 4^8 - 1^0$	$58972 := -5^1 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 7^1 - 2^6$	$59025 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 2^0 + 5^0$
$58942 := -5^2 + 8^1 - 9^4 + 4^8 - 2^4$	$58973 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 7^2 - 3^0$	$59026 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 2^1 - 6^0$
$58943 := -5^1 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 4^3 + 3^3$	$58974 := -5^1 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 7^1 + 4^0$	$59026 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 6^0$
$58944 := -5^3 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 4^2 - 4^1$	$58975 := -5^2 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 7^2 + 5^0$	$59027 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 2^5 - 7^2$
$58945 := -5^2 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 4^2 + 5^0$	$58977 := -5^2 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 7^0 - 7^2$	$59028 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 8^0$
$58946 := -5^2 - 8^1 + 9^5 - 4^3 - 6^1$	$58978 := -5^1 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 7^0 - 8^2$	$59029 := -5^2 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 2^2 + 9^5$
$58947 := -5^1 - 8^2 + 9^5 + 4^2 - 7^2$	$58980 := -5^1 - 8^0 + 9^5 - 8^2 + 0^0$	$59031 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 3^2 - 1^0$
$58948 := -5^2 - 8^0 - 9^4 + 4^8 - 8^0$	$58981 := -5^3 - 8^1 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 1^0$	$59032 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 3^1 - 2^4$
		$59033 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 3^0 + 3^2$
		$59034 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 3^3 - 4^2$
		$59035 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 3^2 + 5^0$

$59036 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 3^3 - 6^2$	$59060 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 6^2 + 0^0$	$59084 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 8^2 - 4^1$
$59037 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 3^0 - 7^1$	$59061 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 1^0$	$59086 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 8^2 - 6^0$
$59038 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 3^0 - 8^1$	$59061 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 1^0$	$59087 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 8^2 - 7^0$
$59038 := 5^2 + 9^4 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 8^5$	$59062 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 2^4$	$59088 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 8^0 + 8^2$
$59039 := -5^1 - 9^0 - 0^0 - 3^1 + 9^5$	$59062 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 6^1 + 2^0$	$59089 := -5^2 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 9^5$
$59040 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 4^2 - 0^0$	$59063 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 3^1$	$59092 := -5^1 + 9^2 - 0^0 + 9^5 - 2^5$
$59040 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 4^2 + 0^0$	$59063 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 3^1$	$59092 := 5^2 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 9^5 + 2^4$
$59041 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 4^2 + 1^0$	$59064 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 4^1$	$59093 := 5^2 + 9^1 + 0^0 + 9^5 + 3^2$
$59042 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 4^0 - 2^1$	$59064 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^2 - 4^2$	$59097 := -5^2 + 9^2 - 0^0 + 9^5 - 7^1$
$59043 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 4^0 - 3^0$	$59065 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 5^1$	$59098 := -5^1 - 9^1 - 0^0 + 9^5 + 8^2$
$59044 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 4^0 - 4^0$	$59065 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 5^1$	$59103 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 0^0 + 3^3$
$59045 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 4^0 - 5^0$	$59066 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 6^1$	$59108 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 1^0 + 0^0 + 8^2$
$59046 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 4^1 - 6^0$	$59066 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 6^2$	$59120 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 2^6 + 0^0$
$59047 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 7^0$	$59067 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 7^1$	$59132 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 1^0 + 3^4 + 2^3$
$59048 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 4^1 - 8^0$	$59067 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 7^1$	$59133 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 1^0 + 3^2 + 3^4$
$59049 := -5^1 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 9^5$	$59068 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 8^1$	$59134 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 1^0 + 3^3 + 4^3$
$59050 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 0^1$	$59068 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 8^1$	$59137 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 3^4 + 7^0$
$59051 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 1^0$	$59069 := 5^1 + 9^1 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 9^5$	$59138 := 5^3 + 9^4 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 8^5$
$59052 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 5^0 + 2^3$	$59069 := -5^2 + 9^1 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 9^5$	$59139 := 5^1 + 9^2 + 1^0 + 3^1 + 9^5$
$59053 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 5^0 + 3^2$	$59071 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 7^2 - 1^0$	$59140 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 4^3 + 0^0$
$59054 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 4^1$	$59072 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 2^4$	$59150 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^3 + 0^1$
$59055 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 5^1$	$59072 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 7^2 - 2^1$	$59151 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^3 + 1^0$
$59056 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 6^1$	$59073 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 3^3$	$59152 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 1^0 + 5^3 - 2^4$
$59056 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 6^0$	$59074 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 7^2 + 4^0$	$59153 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^3 + 3^1$
$59057 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 7^0$	$59075 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 7^1 + 5^2$	$59154 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^3 - 4^2$
$59057 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 7^1$	$59076 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 6^0$	$59155 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 5^3$
$59058 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 8^1$	$59077 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 7^0$	$59156 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^3 + 6^1$
$59059 := -5^1 + 9^1 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 9^5$	$59083 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 3^3$	$59157 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^3 + 7^1$
$59060 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 0^1$	$59084 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 4^0$	$59158 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^4 - 8^3$
		$59159 := -5^1 - 9^1 - 1^0 + 5^3 + 9^5$
		$59172 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 1^0 + 7^0 + 2^7$
		$59173 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 1^0 + 7^2 + 3^4$

$59175 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 1^0 + 7^1 + 5^3$	$59234 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^5 + 3^5 - 4^0$	$59265 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 6^3 + 5^0$
$59177 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 7^0$	$59234 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^0$	$59266 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 6^3 - 6^1$
$59182 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 2^8$	$59236 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^5 + 3^5 + 6^0$	$59267 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 6^3 - 7^0$
$59184 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 4^0$	$59237 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 2^0 + 3^5 - 7^2$	$59267 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 7^2$
$59192 := 5^1 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 9^5 + 2^7$	$59240 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 4^3 + 0^0$	$59268 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^4 + 6^3 - 8^1$
$59193 := 5^3 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 9^5 + 3^2$	$59241 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 1^0$	$59269 := -5^1 + 9^0 + 2^3 + 6^3 + 9^5$
$59202 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 0^1 + 2^6$	$59242 := -5^1 - 9^4 + 2^4 + 4^8 + 2^8$	$59269 := 5^1 + 9^2 + 2^7 + 6^1 + 9^5$
$59203 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 3^0$	$59242 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 2^1$	$59270 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 7^3 + 0^0$
$59203 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^6 + 0^1 + 3^5$	$59243 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^6 + 4^4 + 3^3$	$59272 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 7^3 + 2^2$
$59204 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 0^0 + 4^0$	$59243 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 3^1$	$59273 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^0 + 7^1 + 3^5$
$59205 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 0^1 + 5^2$	$59244 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 4^4 - 4^3$	$59274 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 7^3 - 4^0$
$59207 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 7^0$	$59244 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 4^3$	$59276 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 7^3 + 6^0$
$59208 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 0^0 + 8^0$	$59245 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 5^3$	$59278 := -5^4 + 9^5 - 2^0 + 7^3 + 8^3$
$59222 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 2^5 + 2^7$	$59245 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 4^3 + 5^3$	$59280 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 8^0 - 0^0$
$59223 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 2^8 - 3^4$	$59246 := -5^2 - 9^4 + 2^9 + 4^8 - 6^3$	$59281 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^8 + 8^3 + 1^0$
$59223 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 2^7 + 3^2$	$59246 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 6^1$	$59282 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 2^8$
$59224 := -5^1 - 9^4 - 2^1 + 2^8 + 4^8$	$59247 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^2$	$59282 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 2^4 + 8^2 + 2^7$
$59224 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 4^2$	$59247 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 2^2 + 4^4 - 7^2$	$59283 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 8^2 - 3^4$
$59225 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 2^3 + 2^6 + 5^3$	$59248 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 4^4 - 8^2$	$59283 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 8^2 + 3^4$
$59226 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 2^7 + 6^2$	$59248 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 8^1$	$59284 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 2^4 + 8^3 - 4^4$
$59226 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^4 + 2^1 + 6^3$	$59249 := -5^2 + 9^0 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 9^5$	$59285 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 8^1 + 5^3$
$59227 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^2 + 2^8 - 7^2$	$59249 := 5^3 + 9^1 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 9^5$	$59286 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 8^1 + 6^3$
$59227 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 7^2$	$59260 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 6^3 - 0^0$	$59286 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^8 + 8^3 + 6^1$
$59228 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 2^3 + 2^7 + 8^2$	$59260 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 2^0 + 6^3 + 0^0$	$59287 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 8^1 - 7^0$
$59229 := -5^2 + 9^2 - 2^2 + 2^7 + 9^5$	$59261 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 6^3 - 1^0$	$59288 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^8 + 8^1 + 8^3$
$59230 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 0^0$	$59262 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 6^3 + 2^0$	$59289 := -5^2 + 9^0 + 2^8 + 8^1 + 9^5$
$59230 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 3^5 - 0^0$	$59263 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 6^3 + 3^0$	$59290 := -5^1 - 9^1 + 2^8 + 9^5 - 0^0$
$59232 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 2^0 + 3^4 + 2^7$	$59263 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 6^1 + 3^4$	$59292 := -5^1 - 9^1 + 2^0 + 9^5 + 2^8$
$59233 := -5^4 + 9^5 - 2^0 + 3^4 + 3^6$	$59264 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 6^3 - 4^1$	$59298 := -5^1 - 9^0 + 2^8 + 9^5 - 8^0$
		$59302 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 2^8$
		$59302 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 0^0 + 2^2$
		$59304 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 0^0 + 4^4$

$59307 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 3^4 + 0^0 + 7^3$	$59353 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 5^3 + 3^3$	$59387 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 3^0 + 8^0 + 7^3$
$59312 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 2^8$	$59354 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^6 + 5^4 - 4^5$	$59392 := 5^1 + 9^0 + 3^4 + 9^5 + 2^8$
$59314 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 4^4$	$59355 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 5^3$	$59392 := -5^4 + 9^3 + 3^5 + 9^5 - 2^2$
$59316 := -5^4 + 9^5 + 3^7 + 1^0 - 6^4$	$59356 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 5^1 + 6^3$	$59393 := -5^4 + 9^3 - 3^1 + 9^5 + 3^5$
$59317 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 1^0 + 7^2$	$59356 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^3$	$59394 := 5^1 + 9^2 + 3^1 + 9^5 + 4^4$
$59319 := 5^2 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 1^0 + 9^5$	$59357 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 3^5 + 5^4 - 7^2$	$59394 := -5^3 + 9^3 - 3^1 + 9^5 - 4^4$
$59320 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 2^8 + 0^0$	$59357 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^2$	$59395 := -5^4 + 9^3 + 3^5 + 9^5 - 5^0$
$59320 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 2^5 + 0^0$	$59359 := -5^4 + 9^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 9^5$	$59396 := -5^4 - 9^2 - 3^5 + 9^5 + 6^4$
$59322 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 2^0 + 2^2$	$59362 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 6^0 + 2^6$	$59397 := -5^1 + 9^0 + 3^2 + 9^5 + 7^3$
$59326 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 2^8 - 6^0$	$59362 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 6^0 + 2^8$	$59399 := 5^2 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 9^2 + 9^5$
$59326 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 2^3 + 6^0$	$59367 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 6^0 + 7^2$	$59405 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 0^1 + 5^3$
$59328 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 2^8 + 8^0$	$59367 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 3^0 + 6^0 + 7^3$	$59406 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 0^1 + 6^3$
$59332 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 3^5 + 2^5$	$59368 := -5^4 + 9^5 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^0$	$59409 := -5^4 + 9^3 + 4^4 + 0^1 + 9^5$
$59332 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 3^5 + 2^6$	$59369 := -5^1 + 9^2 + 3^5 + 6^0 + 9^5$	$59420 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 4^2 + 2^9 + 0^1$
$59333 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 3^3 + 3^5$	$59370 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 7^3 + 0^1$	$59421 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 4^2 + 2^9 + 1^0$
$59334 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 3^1 + 4^4$	$59371 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 7^3 + 1^0$	$59422 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 4^2 + 2^1 + 2^9$
$59334 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 3^5 + 4^3$	$59372 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 7^3 - 2^4$	$59423 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 2^5 + 3^4$
$59335 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 3^3 + 5^3$	$59373 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 7^2 + 3^5$	$59423 := -5^2 - 9^4 + 4^8 - 2^8 + 3^6$
$59336 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 3^5 + 6^2$	$59373 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 7^3 + 3^1$	$59424 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 2^7 + 4^4$
$59337 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 3^5 + 7^2$	$59374 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 7^3 - 4^2$	$59425 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 4^4 + 2^9 + 5^3$
$59337 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 3^4 + 7^0$	$59375 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 7^3 + 5^1$	$59426 := -5^2 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 2^9 - 6^2$
$59339 := -5^2 - 9^1 + 3^4 + 3^5 + 9^5$	$59375 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 7^2 + 5^3$	$59426 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 2^5 + 6^3$
$59339 := 5^3 + 9^2 + 3^1 + 3^4 + 9^5$	$59376 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 7^3 + 6^1$	$59427 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 2^7 - 7^0$
$59340 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 3^6 + 4^5 + 0^0$	$59377 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 3^1 + 7^3 - 7^1$	$59428 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 2^8 + 8^2$
$59340 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 0^0$	$59378 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 3^0 + 7^3 - 8^1$	$59429 := -5^1 + 9^0 + 4^4 + 2^7 + 9^5$
$59347 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 7^2$	$59379 := -5^1 + 9^0 - 3^2 + 7^3 + 9^5$	$59432 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 2^8$
$59349 := -5^2 + 9^2 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 9^5$	$59379 := 5^1 + 9^2 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 9^5$	$59434 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 4^4$
$59352 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 2^8$	$59382 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 8^0 + 2^8$	$59436 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 4^0 + 3^6 - 6^3$
$59353 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 5^1 + 3^5$	$59382 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 8^0 + 2^6$	$59438 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 8^3$

$59443 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 4^4 + 3^2$	$59498 := -5^2 + 9^3 - 4^4 + 9^5 + 8^0$	$59568 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 8^3$
$59444 := -5^7 + 9^4 - 4^3 + 4^8 + 4^8$	$59512 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 5^2 + 1^0 + 2^9$	$59569 := -5^2 - 9^2 + 5^4 + 6^0 + 9^5$
$59445 := -5^4 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 4^5 + 5^0$	$59516 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 1^0 + 6^3$	$59572 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 2^9$
$59446 := -5^4 + 9^5 - 4^0 + 4^5 - 6^0$	$59522 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 2^0 - 2^7$	$59572 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 7^1 + 2^4$
$59447 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 4^3 + 7^3$	$59523 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 2^0 - 3^3$	$59573 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 7^3 + 3^4$
$59447 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 7^0$	$59525 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 5^3 + 2^0 + 5^4$	$59574 := -5^2 - 9^4 + 5^4 - 7^0 + 4^8$
$59448 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 4^2 + 8^3$	$59529 := -5^3 + 9^3 - 5^3 + 2^0 + 9^5$	$59575 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 7^0 + 5^4$
$59450 := -5^4 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 0^0$	$59532 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 5^2 + 3^0 + 2^9$	$59578 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 8^3$
$59452 := -5^4 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 2^0$	$59534 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 3^0 - 4^2$	$59578 := -5^6 - 9^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^3$
$59454 := -5^4 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 4^5$	$59536 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 5^0 + 3^6 - 6^3$	$59580 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 8^3 - 0^0$
$59455 := -5^5 + 9^2 - 4^0 + 5^7 - 5^6$	$59537 := -5^4 - 9^5 - 5^4 + 3^7 + 7^6$	$59582 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 8^0 + 2^9$
$59456 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^0$	$59538 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 8^3$	$59583 := -5^6 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 8^0 - 3^7$
$59462 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^3 + 2^7$	$59539 := -5^3 - 9^0 + 5^4 - 3^2 + 9^5$	$59586 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 8^0 + 6^2$
$59462 := -5^4 + 9^5 - 4^4 + 6^4 - 2^1$	$59542 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 4^0 - 2^7$	$59588 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 8^3$
$59463 := -5^2 - 9^4 + 4^8 - 6^3 + 3^6$	$59543 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 4^0 + 3^5$	$59589 := -5^1 - 9^2 + 5^4 + 8^0 + 9^5$
$59463 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^3 + 3^2$	$59545 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 5^3 + 4^0 + 5^4$	$59592 := 5^1 + 9^0 + 5^2 + 9^5 + 2^9$
$59465 := -5^4 + 9^5 - 4^4 + 6^4 + 5^0$	$59549 := -5^3 - 9^0 + 5^4 + 4^0 + 9^5$	$59592 := -5^1 - 9^2 + 5^4 + 9^5 + 2^2$
$59467 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 7^3$	$59550 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 0^1$	$59593 := -5^6 - 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^1 - 3^7$
$59467 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 6^3 - 7^2$	$59551 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 1^0$	$59594 := -5^1 - 9^0 + 5^4 - 9^4 + 4^8$
$59468 := -5^2 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 6^1 + 8^3$	$59552 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 5^1 + 5^0 + 2^9$	$59596 := -5^2 - 9^3 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 6^4$
$59479 := 5^1 + 9^2 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 9^5$	$59552 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 5^3 + 2^7$	$59596 := 5^3 + 9^2 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 6^3$
$59481 := -5^1 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 8^3 - 1^0$	$59553 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 5^3 + 5^4 + 3^2$	$59597 := -5^3 - 9^0 + 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2$
$59483 := -5^1 + 9^0 + 4^8 + 8^3 - 3^8$	$59554 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 4^1$	$59602 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 0^1 + 2^9$
$59484 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 4^2 + 8^3 + 4^3$	$59555 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 5^4$	$59604 := -5^5 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 0^1 - 4^6$
$59486 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 4^3 + 8^3 - 6^1$	$59556 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 6^1$	$59606 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 6^3$
$59487 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 7^2$	$59557 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 7^1$	$59622 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 2^8 + 2^8$
$59488 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 4^1 + 8^3 - 8^2$	$59558 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 8^3$	$59623 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 2^9 + 3^4$
$59496 := -5^2 + 9^3 - 4^4 + 9^5 - 6^0$	$59559 := -5^3 + 9^1 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 9^5$	$59623 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 2^9 + 3^0$
$59497 := -5^4 + 9^3 + 4^0 + 9^5 + 7^3$	$59562 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 2^9$	$59624 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 2^7 + 4^4$
		$59625 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 6^2 + 2^9 + 5^3$
		$59628 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 6^2 + 2^7 + 8^3$
		$59629 := -5^4 + 9^3 - 6^2 + 2^9 + 9^5$

$59634 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 3^5 + 4^0$	$59689 := 5^4 + 9^0 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 9^5$	$59756 := -5^3 + 9^0 - 7^4 + 5^6 + 6^6$
$59638 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 3^4 + 8^3$	$59690 := -5^3 + 9^3 + 6^2 + 9^5 + 0^0$	$59757 := -5^2 - 9^5 + 7^5 - 5^6 + 7^6$
$59638 := 5^4 + 9^4 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 8^5$	$59690 := 5^4 + 9^1 + 6^1 + 9^5 + 0^0$	$59759 := -5^1 - 9^1 - 7^4 + 5^5 + 9^5$
$59642 := -5^4 - 9^4 + 6^4 + 4^8 - 2^2$	$59692 := 5^4 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 2^4$	$59760 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 6^2 + 0^0$
$59643 := -5^2 + 9^3 - 6^2 + 4^8 - 3^8$	$59693 := -5^1 - 9^2 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 3^6$	$59763 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 3^4$
$59645 := -5^4 - 9^4 + 6^4 + 4^8 - 5^0$	$59693 := 5^4 + 9^1 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 3^2$	$59768 := -5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 6^4 - 8^0$
$59647 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 4^3 + 7^3$	$59703 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 0^0 + 3^6$	$59772 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 2^5$
$59647 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 4^4 + 7^0$	$59703 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 3^3$	$59772 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 7^1 + 7^3 + 2^9$
$59648 := -5^2 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 4^7 - 8^4$	$59725 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 2^0 + 5^0$	$59773 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^0 + 7^0 + 3^6$
$59650 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 0^1$	$59726 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 2^1 + 6^0$	$59773 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 3^0$
$59651 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 1^0$	$59728 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 2^2 + 8^0$	$59774 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^3 + 7^2 + 4^5$
$59652 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 6^0 + 5^4 - 2^4$	$59732 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^2 + 3^6 + 2^3$	$59774 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 7^3 + 4^4$
$59653 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 3^1$	$59732 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 2^3$	$59775 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^4 + 7^1 + 5^5$
$59654 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 - 4^2$	$59733 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^2 + 3^2 + 3^6$	$59776 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 6^2$
$59655 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^1 + 5^4$	$59733 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 3^2$	$59776 := -5^4 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 7^2 + 6^4$
$59656 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 6^1$	$59734 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 3^4 + 4^4$	$59778 := -5^3 + 9^5 - 7^0 + 7^3 + 8^3$
$59657 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 7^1$	$59734 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^3 + 3^2 + 4^5$	$59779 := -5^1 + 9^3 - 7^0 + 7^1 + 9^5$
$59658 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4 + 8^1$	$59735 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 3^6 - 5^2$	$59780 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 8^3 + 0^0$
$59659 := -5^1 - 9^1 - 6^0 + 5^4 + 9^5$	$59736 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^0 + 3^6 - 6^2$	$59788 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 8^0 + 8^2$
$59662 := -5^4 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 6^4 - 2^6$	$59736 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 3^1 + 6^3$	$59790 := 5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 0^1$
$59674 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 4^4$	$59737 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 3^3 + 7^3$	$59791 := 5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 1^0$
$59675 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 6^0 + 7^1 + 5^4$	$59738 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 7^1 + 3^6 - 8^1$	$59792 := 5^1 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 2^3$
$59677 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 7^0$	$59738 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 3^1 + 8^3$	$59792 := -5^2 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 2^5$
$59682 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 8^0 + 2^0$	$59739 := -5^4 + 9^3 + 7^3 + 3^5 + 9^5$	$59793 := 5^1 + 9^1 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 3^6$
$59683 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 8^3 + 3^4$	$59740 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 4^3 + 0^0$	$59793 := -5^1 + 9^3 - 7^1 + 9^5 + 3^3$
$59683 := -5^4 + 9^2 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$59746 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 4^3 + 6^0$	$59794 := 5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 4^1$
$59684 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 4^0$	$59752 := -5^1 + 9^5 - 7^4 + 5^5 - 2^4$	$59795 := 5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 5^1$
$59688 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 8^3 - 8^2$	$59752 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 5^4 + 2^2$	$59796 := 5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 6^1$
$59688 := 5^3 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 8^3$	$59753 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 7^0 + 5^0 + 3^6$	$59796 := -5^2 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 6^2$
		$59797 := 5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 7^1$
		$59798 := 5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 8^1$
		$59798 := -5^2 - 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 8^3$

$59799 := 5^1 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 9^3 + 9^5$	$59932 := 5^2 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 3^6 + 2^7$	$60144 := -6^4 - 0^0 + 1^0 - 4^6 + 4^8$
$59802 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 0^1 + 2^6$	$59932 := -5^2 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^5 - 2^6$	$60289 := 6^3 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 8^3 + 9^5$
$59822 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 2^7 + 2^7$	$59933 := 5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 3^3$	$60294 := -6^2 + 0^0 + 2^8 + 9^5 + 4^5$
$59823 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 3^6$	$59934 := 5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 4^1$	$60294 := 6^3 + 0^0 + 2^2 + 9^5 + 4^5$
$59824 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 2^1 + 4^4$	$59935 := 5^1 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 5^3$	$60349 := 6^4 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 9^5$
$59824 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 2^5 + 4^4$	$59936 := -5^1 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 3^7 - 6^4$	$60359 := 6^4 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 9^5$
$59827 := -5^5 - 9^5 + 8^4 + 2^8 + 7^6$	$59936 := 5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 6^1$	$60379 := 6^4 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 7^1 + 9^5$
$59829 := -5^1 + 9^3 - 8^1 + 2^6 + 9^5$	$59937 := 5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 7^1$	$60395 := -6^3 + 0^1 + 3^7 + 9^5 - 5^4$
$59830 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 3^5 + 0^0$	$59937 := -5^7 + 9^0 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 7^6$	$60397 := 6^4 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 9^5 + 7^2$
$59833 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 8^0 + 3^4 + 3^6$	$59938 := 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 8^3$	$60397 := -6^4 + 0^1 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 7^4$
$59834 := -5^6 + 9^5 - 8^0 + 3^3 + 4^7$	$59938 := -5^5 - 9^0 + 9^5 - 3^4 + 8^4$	$60409 := 6^4 + 0^1 + 4^3 + 0^1 + 9^5$
$59836 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 3^6 - 6^0$	$59939 := 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^3 + 3^3 + 9^5$	$60435 := -6^4 - 0^0 - 4^7 - 3^2 + 5^7$
$59838 := -5^1 + 9^5 + 8^0 + 3^6 + 8^2$	$59940 := -5^3 - 9^1 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 0^0$	$60445 := -6^4 - 0^0 + 4^0 - 4^7 + 5^7$
$59843 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 4^3 + 3^5$	$59940 := 5^4 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 0^0$	$60452 := -6^4 - 0^0 - 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^3$
$59843 := 5^2 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 3^0$	$59946 := -5^3 - 9^0 + 9^5 + 4^5 - 6^0$	$60453 := -6^4 - 0^0 - 4^7 + 5^7 + 3^2$
$59846 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 4^3 + 6^3$	$59948 := -5^3 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 4^5 - 8^0$	$60483 := 6^5 + 0^1 + 4^4 + 8^5 + 3^9$
$59863 := 5^1 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 6^3 + 3^4$	$59948 := -5^3 - 9^0 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 8^0$	$60487 := -6^4 + 0^1 + 4^8 - 8^4 + 7^3$
$59878 := -5^2 + 9^5 - 8^0 + 7^3 + 8^3$	$59953 := -5^2 - 9^1 + 9^5 + 5^5 - 3^7$	$60494 := -6^3 - 0^0 - 4^6 - 9^3 + 4^8$
$59883 := 5^4 + 9^5 + 8^2 + 8^2 + 3^4$	$59954 := -5^3 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 4^5$	$60593 := 6^4 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^5$
$59884 := -5^3 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 8^3 - 4^3$	$59957 := 5^1 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 7^2$	$60595 := 6^4 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 5^3$
$59887 := -5^2 + 9^5 + 8^1 + 8^3 + 7^3$	$59959 := -5^2 + 9^2 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 9^5$	$60845 := -6^7 + 0^1 + 8^3 + 4^9 + 5^7$
$59902 := -5^1 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 2^7$	$59968 := -5^2 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 6^3 - 8^0$	$60853 := 6^5 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 5^4 + 3^9$
$59904 := 5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 4^0$	$59968 := 5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 8^2$	$60859 := 6^4 + 0^0 + 8^3 + 5^0 + 9^5$
$59905 := 5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^0$	$59974 := -5^2 - 9^2 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 4^5$	$60885 := -6^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 5^5$
$59912 := 5^1 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 2^7$	$59974 := 5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 7^1 + 4^3$	$60922 := 6^4 + 0^0 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 2^9$
$59913 := 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 3^6$	$59976 := -5^2 - 9^0 + 9^5 - 7^3 + 6^4$	$60938 := 6^4 + 0^1 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 8^3$
$59920 := 5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 2^4 + 0^0$	$59992 := 5^1 + 9^2 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 2^7$	$60939 := -6^3 + 0^1 - 9^2 + 3^7 + 9^5$
$59930 := 5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 0^1$	$59993 := 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^2 + 9^5 + 3^6$	$60943 := -6^2 - 0^0 + 9^5 - 4^4 + 3^7$
$59931 := 5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 1^0$	$59997 := -5^3 + 9^0 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 7^3$	$60959 := -6^4 + 0^1 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 9^5$
		$60965 := -6^1 + 0^0 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 5^4$
		$61239 := -6^1 + 1^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 9^5$
		$61293 := -6^1 - 1^0 + 2^6 + 9^5 + 3^7$

$61297 := -6^3 - 1^0 + 2^6 + 9^5 + 7^4$	$62159 := -6^1 - 2^3 - 1^0 + 5^5 + 9^5$	$62395 := 6^3 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 9^5 + 5^5$
$61329 := -6^2 + 1^0 + 3^7 + 2^7 + 9^5$	$62167 := -6^4 + 2^0 - 1^0 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$62396 := 6^4 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 6^4$
$61404 := -6^2 - 1^0 - 4^6 + 0^0 + 4^8$	$62167 := -6^4 - 2^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$62397 := 6^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 7^4$
$61434 := -6^1 - 1^0 - 4^6 + 3^0 + 4^8$	$62176 := -6^4 + 2^3 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 6^6$	$62405 := -6^1 - 2^0 + 4^8 + 0^0 - 5^5$
$61438 := -6^1 + 1^0 + 4^8 + 3^1 - 8^4$	$62179 := 6^3 + 2^9 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 9^5$	$62407 := -6^3 - 2^9 + 4^8 + 0^1 - 7^4$
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$61475 := -6^3 - 1^0 - 4^7 - 7^2 + 5^7$	$62264 := -6^4 + 2^3 + 2^9 + 6^6 + 4^7$	$62428 := -6^2 + 2^9 + 4^8 + 2^9 - 8^4$
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$61839 := -6^4 - 1^0 + 8^4 - 3^2 + 9^5$	$62315 := 6^6 + 2^5 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 5^6$	$62463 := -6^2 + 2^8 - 4^6 + 6^6 + 3^9$
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$61849 := -6^4 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 4^6 + 9^5$	$62347 := -6^5 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^8 + 7^4$	$62467 := -6^2 + 2^6 - 4^5 + 6^6 + 7^5$
$61854 := -6^5 - 1^0 + 8^4 - 5^0 + 4^8$	$62352 := 6^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 2^6$	$62469 := -6^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^6 + 9^3$
$61895 := -6^3 + 1^0 - 8^2 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$62354 := -6^3 + 2^5 - 3^9 + 5^7 + 4^6$	$62479 := -6^3 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 7^6 - 9^5$
$61897 := -6^4 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 9^5 + 7^2$	$62354 := 6^6 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 4^3$	$62485 := -6^1 + 2^4 + 4^8 + 8^2 - 5^5$
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$61927 := -6^2 + 1^0 + 9^5 + 2^9 + 7^4$	$62356 := -6^5 + 2^9 - 3^6 + 5^7 - 6^5$	$62504 := -6^2 + 2^7 - 5^5 + 0^0 + 4^8$
$61956 := -6^3 - 1^0 + 9^5 + 5^5 - 6^0$	$62358 := 6^6 + 2^2 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 8^2$	$62506 := 6^3 + 2^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 6^6$
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$62056 := -6^3 - 2^3 - 0^0 + 5^6 + 6^6$	$62376 := -6^4 + 2^7 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6$	$62533 := 6^6 + 2^3 + 5^6 + 3^0 + 3^5$
$62065 := -6^3 + 2^0 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 5^6$	$62394 := 6^1 + 2^7 + 3^7 + 9^5 + 4^5$	$62534 := -6^1 + 2^7 - 5^5 + 3^0 + 4^8$
$62065 := -6^3 - 2^0 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 5^6$	$62394 := -6^1 - 2^4 - 3^6 + 9^5 + 4^6$	$62535 := -6^1 + 2^5 - 5^6 + 3^2 + 5^7$
$62155 := -6^3 - 2^7 - 1^0 - 5^6 + 5^7$	$62395 := -6^1 - 2^4 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$62535 := 6^6 + 2^7 + 5^3 + 3^0 + 5^6$

$62540 := 6^6 + 2^1 + 5^6 + 4^4 + 0^0$	$62645 := -6^5 + 2^3 - 6^5 + 4^3 + 5^7$	$62795 := 6^6 + 2^9 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 5^6$
$62542 := 6^6 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 4^1 + 2^8$	$62647 := -6^3 - 2^7 + 6^6 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$62797 := 6^4 + 2^1 + 7^2 + 9^5 + 7^4$
$62546 := 6^6 + 2^3 + 5^6 + 4^4 + 6^0$	$62648 := -6^3 + 2^7 + 6^4 + 4^8 - 8^4$	$62798 := -6^1 + 2^1 - 7^3 + 9^5 + 8^4$
$62553 := -6^1 + 2^5 - 5^6 + 5^7 + 3^3$	$62649 := -6^3 - 2^6 - 6^3 + 4^6 + 9^5$	$62825 := 6^6 + 2^4 + 8^3 + 2^4 + 5^6$
$62553 := 6^6 + 2^2 + 5^2 + 5^6 + 3^5$	$62653 := -6^5 - 2^0 - 6^5 + 5^7 + 3^4$	$62843 := -6^4 + 2^9 - 8^4 + 4^8 + 3^7$
$62554 := -6^1 - 2^2 - 5^6 + 5^7 + 4^3$	$62653 := 6^6 + 2^7 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 3^5$	$62845 := -6^2 - 2^6 - 8^6 - 4^8 + 5^8$
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$62555 := -6^1 - 2^6 + 5^3 - 5^6 + 5^7$	$62664 := -6^3 - 2^6 - 6^4 - 6^4 + 4^8$	$62849 := -6^2 - 2^2 + 8^4 - 4^4 + 9^5$
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$62557 := -6^1 + 2^6 - 5^6 + 5^7 - 7^0$	$62684 := -6^2 - 2^4 + 6^4 - 8^4 + 4^8$	$62864 := -6^3 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 6^6 + 4^7$
$62558 := -6^1 + 2^7 - 5^6 + 5^7 - 8^2$	$62685 := -6^4 - 2^8 - 6^6 + 8^5 + 5^7$	$62867 := -6^1 + 2^8 + 8^5 + 6^6 - 7^5$
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$62562 := 6^3 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 6^6 + 2^6$	$62688 := -6^4 - 2^8 - 6^4 + 8^5 + 8^5$	$62879 := -6^3 - 2^0 + 8^4 - 7^2 + 9^5$
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$62564 := -6^5 - 2^3 + 5^7 - 6^5 - 4^0$	$62689 := -6^2 - 2^2 + 6^5 - 8^4 + 9^5$	$62889 := -6^3 - 2^5 - 8^1 + 8^4 + 9^5$
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$62568 := -6^5 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 6^5 - 8^0$	$62697 := -6^2 - 2^0 + 6^6 - 9^3 + 7^5$	$62898 := -6^3 - 2^5 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 8^4$
$62575 := -6^1 + 2^5 - 5^6 + 7^2 + 5^7$	$62706 := -6^5 - 2^9 + 7^6 + 0^0 - 6^6$	$62914 := -6^3 - 2^4 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 4^6$
$62576 := -6^1 - 2^5 + 5^7 - 7^5 + 6^4$	$62736 := -6^3 - 2^9 + 7^5 + 3^0 + 6^6$	$62924 := -6^3 - 2^0 + 9^5 - 2^2 + 4^6$
$62587 := 6^6 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 8^0 + 7^2$	$62749 := 6^4 + 2^1 + 7^4 + 4^0 + 9^5$	$62928 := -6^3 - 2^1 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 8^4$
$62594 := 6^2 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 4^4$	$62752 := 6^6 + 2^6 + 7^3 + 5^6 + 2^6$	$62934 := -6^2 - 2^8 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 4^6$
$62595 := -6^3 + 2^9 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$62753 := 6^6 + 2^7 + 7^3 + 5^6 + 3^0$	$62935 := 6^1 + 2^9 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 5^5$
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$62605 := -6^5 + 2^5 - 6^5 + 0^1 + 5^7$	$62776 := -6^3 - 2^7 - 7^3 + 7^5 + 6^6$	$62958 := -6^3 + 2^2 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 8^4$
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$62625 := 6^3 + 2^6 + 6^6 + 2^6 + 5^6$	$62794 := -6^1 - 2^1 - 7^3 + 9^5 + 4^6$	$62974 := -6^2 - 2^7 + 9^5 - 7^1 + 4^6$
$62643 := -6^5 - 2^4 + 6^6 + 4^6 + 3^9$	$62794 := 6^4 + 2^5 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 4^2$	$62980 := -6^2 - 2^7 + 9^5 + 8^4 - 0^0$
		$62982 := -6^2 + 2^0 + 9^5 + 8^4 - 2^7$
		$62985 := -6^2 + 2^0 + 9^5 + 8^4 - 5^3$
		$62994 := -6^1 - 2^6 - 9^2 + 9^5 + 4^6$

$62995 := -6^2 + 2^7 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$63274 := -6^2 - 3^4 + 2^8 - 7^4 + 4^8$	$63389 := 6^3 + 3^0 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 9^5$
$62997 := -6^3 + 2^2 + 9^4 + 9^5 - 7^4$	$63275 := -6^5 - 3^8 - 2^9 - 7^0 + 5^7$	$63407 := -6^6 - 3^8 - 4^5 - 0^0 + 7^6$
$63042 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 2^0$	$63276 := -6^3 - 3^1 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 6^6$	$63408 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 8^2$
$63043 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 3^0$	$63293 := 6^4 + 3^6 + 2^5 + 9^5 + 3^7$	$63412 := 6^6 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 2^7$
$63044 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 0^1 + 4^0 + 4^7$	$63294 := -6^1 + 3^3 + 2^7 + 9^5 + 4^6$	$63423 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 3^4$
$63045 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 5^0$	$63294 := 6^2 + 3^4 + 2^5 + 9^5 + 4^6$	$63429 := -6^4 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 - 9^3$
$63047 := -6^1 - 3^4 - 0^0 + 4^8 - 7^4$	$63304 := -6^2 - 3^2 - 3^7 + 0^1 + 4^8$	$63430 := -6^4 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 3^6 + 0^1$
$63054 := 6^6 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 4^7$	$63324 := -6^1 - 3^1 - 3^7 - 2^4 + 4^8$	$63431 := -6^4 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 3^6 + 1^0$
$63059 := -6^5 - 3^6 + 0^1 + 5^7 - 9^4$	$63324 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 3^3 + 2^8 + 4^7$	$63432 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 2^3$
$63074 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 4^7$	$63329 := -6^4 - 3^6 + 3^8 - 2^8 + 9^5$	$63433 := -6^1 + 3^2 + 4^8 + 3^4 - 3^7$
$63124 := -6^3 - 3^7 - 1^0 - 2^3 + 4^8$	$63340 := -6^1 - 3^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 0^1$	$63434 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 3^3 + 4^8$
$63124 := 6^6 + 3^4 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 4^7$	$63341 := -6^1 - 3^0 - 3^7 + 4^8 - 1^0$	$63435 := -6^2 - 3^1 + 4^8 - 3^7 + 5^3$
$63142 := -6^3 - 3^7 + 1^0 + 4^8 + 2^3$	$63342 := -6^1 + 3^0 - 3^7 + 4^8 - 2^1$	$63435 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 3^5 + 5^3$
$63143 := -6^3 + 3^2 + 1^0 + 4^8 - 3^7$	$63342 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 2^5$	$63436 := -6^4 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 3^6 + 6^1$
$63149 := -6^1 + 3^2 + 1^0 + 4^6 + 9^5$	$63343 := -6^1 - 3^0 + 3^0 + 4^8 - 3^7$	$63436 := 6^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 3^8 + 6^6$
$63149 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 1^0 + 4^7 + 9^2$	$63344 := -6^1 - 3^1 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 4^8$	$63437 := -6^4 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 3^6 + 7^1$
$63167 := -6^3 - 3^4 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$63345 := -6^1 + 3^0 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 5^0$	$63437 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 3^3 + 7^3$
$63189 := -6^2 + 3^4 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 9^5$	$63346 := -6^1 - 3^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 6^1$	$63438 := -6^3 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 3^7 - 8^4$
$63214 := -6^1 - 3^7 - 2^7 - 1^0 + 4^8$	$63346 := 6^2 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 6^6$	$63438 := 6^5 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 3^9 + 8^5$
$63234 := -6^2 - 3^4 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^8$	$63347 := -6^1 + 3^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 7^0$	$63439 := -6^4 - 3^4 + 4^8 + 3^2 - 9^3$
$63234 := 6^6 + 3^4 + 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^7$	$63348 := -6^1 - 3^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 8^1$	$63442 := -6^2 - 3^7 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 2^7$
$63239 := -6^3 + 3^7 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 9^5$	$63348 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 8^2$	$63446 := -6^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 4^8 - 6^0$
$63244 := -6^4 + 3^3 + 2^0 + 4^8 - 4^5$	$63349 := -6^1 - 3^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 9^1$	$63448 := -6^4 - 3^6 + 4^0 + 4^8 - 8^2$
$63246 := -6^2 + 3^5 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^6$	$63364 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 3^3 - 6^1 + 4^8$	$63452 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 5^3 - 2^4$
$63248 := -6^2 - 3^7 - 2^0 + 4^8 - 8^2$	$63364 := 6^3 + 3^3 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 4^7$	$63453 := -6^4 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 3^4$
$63254 := -6^1 - 3^7 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 4^8$	$63367 := -6^1 - 3^2 - 3^4 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$63454 := -6^2 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 4^8$
$63254 := 6^6 + 3^4 + 2^3 + 5^3 + 4^7$	$63368 := -6^4 - 3^7 + 3^9 + 6^6 + 8^3$	$63455 := -6^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^7 - 5^6$
$63255 := -6^1 + 3^6 + 2^5 + 5^7 - 5^6$	$63369 := -6^3 - 3^6 + 3^8 - 6^4 + 9^5$	$63457 := -6^4 - 3^6 + 4^8 - 5^1 - 7^2$
$63257 := -6^3 + 3^7 - 2^5 + 5^7 - 7^5$	$63384 := -6^3 - 3^3 + 3^7 - 8^4 + 4^8$	$63457 := 6^6 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^2$
		$63458 := -6^3 + 3^6 - 4^8 + 5^8 - 8^6$
		$63459 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 5^3 - 9^1$
		$63467 := -6^1 + 3^2 + 4^0 + 6^6 + 7^5$

$63470 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 0^1$	$63497 := 6^1 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 7^3$	$63570 := 6^6 + 3^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 0^0$
$63471 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 1^0$	$63497 := -6^5 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 9^5 + 7^4$	$63584 := -6^5 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 8^3 + 4^8$
$63472 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 2^7$	$63498 := 6^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 8^5$	$63584 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 8^3 + 4^7$
$63472 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 2^2$	$63499 := -6^4 - 3^1 + 4^8 - 9^1 - 9^3$	$63585 := -6^6 - 3^3 - 5^4 + 8^5 + 5^7$
$63473 := -6^1 + 3^4 + 4^8 + 7^2 - 3^7$	$63508 := -6^6 - 3^6 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 8^5$	$63586 := -6^3 + 3^1 - 5^6 + 8^5 + 6^6$
$63473 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 3^1$	$63522 := 6^6 + 3^6 + 5^6 + 2^8 + 2^8$	$63586 := 6^4 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 8^1 + 6^6$
$63474 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 4^1$	$63523 := -6^5 - 3^2 + 5^7 - 2^8 - 3^8$	$63588 := -6^4 - 3^3 - 5^4 + 8^5 + 8^5$
$63475 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 7^1 + 5^3$	$63523 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 2^9 + 3^6$	$63589 := -6^6 + 3^4 + 5^7 + 8^5 - 9^3$
$63475 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 5^1$	$63524 := -6^4 - 3^3 - 5^4 - 2^6 + 4^8$	$63605 := 6^4 + 3^3 + 6^6 + 0^0 + 5^6$
$63476 := 6^1 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 6^6$	$63525 := -6^3 + 3^6 - 5^6 + 2^9 + 5^7$	$63634 := -6^3 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 3^6 + 4^7$
$63476 := -6^1 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 7^5 + 6^6$	$63526 := -6^1 - 3^8 + 5^7 - 2^8 - 6^5$	$63637 := 6^5 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 7^4$
$63477 := -6^3 - 3^7 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 7^3$	$63527 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 7^5$	$63647 := -6^3 + 3^6 - 6^0 + 4^8 - 7^4$
$63477 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^1 + 7^5$	$63529 := 6^4 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 2^5 + 9^5$	$63648 := -6^4 - 3^4 + 6^0 + 4^8 - 8^3$
$63478 := -6^4 - 3^5 + 4^8 - 7^1 - 8^3$	$63529 := -6^5 - 3^1 + 5^7 - 2^8 - 9^4$	$63653 := -6^3 + 3^4 - 6^5 + 5^7 - 3^8$
$63478 := 6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 8^1$	$63542 := -6^4 - 3^2 - 5^4 + 4^8 - 2^6$	$63654 := -6^2 - 3^7 + 6^3 + 5^3 + 4^8$
$63479 := -6^1 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 7^3 + 9^5$	$63543 := -6^4 + 3^2 - 5^4 + 4^8 - 3^4$	$63659 := 6^4 + 3^0 + 6^6 + 5^6 + 9^2$
$63479 := 6^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 9^5$	$63544 := -6^2 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 4^4 + 4^8$	$63670 := -6^2 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 0^1$
$63483 := -6^4 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 8^0 - 3^6$	$63544 := 6^6 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 4^4 + 4^7$	$63671 := -6^2 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 1^0$
$63484 := -6^4 - 3^5 - 4^0 - 8^3 + 4^8$	$63545 := -6^1 + 3^3 - 5^6 + 4^5 + 5^7$	$63672 := -6^2 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 2^1$
$63485 := -6^4 - 3^6 + 4^8 - 8^0 - 5^2$	$63546 := -6^4 - 3^6 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 6^2$	$63673 := -6^1 - 3^3 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 3^5$
$63486 := -6^4 - 3^5 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 6^0$	$63547 := -6^3 + 3^1 + 5^4 + 4^8 - 7^4$	$63674 := -6^2 - 3^2 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 4^4$
$63492 := 6^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 2^7$	$63548 := -6^4 - 3^1 - 5^4 + 4^8 - 8^2$	$63675 := 6^1 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 5^3$
$63492 := -6^4 - 3^1 + 4^8 - 9^3 - 2^4$	$63549 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 9^2$	$63675 := -6^1 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 7^5 - 5^2$
$63493 := 6^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 9^5 + 3^7$	$63549 := 6^2 + 3^5 + 5^3 + 4^6 + 9^5$	$63676 := -6^1 + 3^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 6^6$
$63493 := -6^4 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 9^1 - 3^6$	$63563 := -6^3 - 3^2 + 5^7 - 6^5 - 3^8$	$63677 := -6^2 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 7^5$
$63494 := -6^4 - 3^0 - 4^2 - 9^3 + 4^8$	$63564 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 4^8$	$63678 := -6^2 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 8^1$
$63495 := 6^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 5^3$	$63566 := -6^1 - 3^8 + 5^7 - 6^3 - 6^5$	$63679 := 6^1 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 + 9^5$
$63495 := -6^4 - 3^6 + 4^8 + 9^1 - 5^2$	$63568 := 6^3 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 6^5 + 8^5$	$63679 := -6^2 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 9^1$
$63496 := -6^1 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 9^3 - 6^4$	$63569 := -6^3 - 3^1 + 5^7 - 6^5 - 9^4$	$63692 := 6^5 + 3^7 + 6^6 + 9^4 + 2^9$
		$63692 := -6^5 + 3^9 - 6^5 + 9^5 + 2^9$
		$63693 := -6^3 - 3^6 + 6^5 + 9^5 - 3^7$
		$63694 := -6^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 + 9^5 + 4^6$

$63695 := -6^1 + 3^0 + 6^5 + 9^5 - 5^5$	$63746 := -6^3 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 4^4 + 6^6$	$63869 := -6^1 + 3^6 + 8^4 + 6^0 + 9^5$
$63695 := 6^3 + 3^2 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$63747 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 7^0 + 4^4 + 7^5$	$63874 := -6^2 - 3^7 + 8^3 + 7^2 + 4^8$
$63697 := -6^1 - 3^6 - 6^6 - 9^4 + 7^6$	$63748 := -6^4 + 3^3 - 7^1 + 4^8 - 8^3$	$63875 := -6^4 - 3^5 + 8^4 - 7^5 + 5^7$
$63697 := 6^3 + 3^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^5$	$63760 := 6^3 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 0^1$	$63876 := -6^2 + 3^8 + 8^5 + 7^5 + 6^5$
$63703 := -6^6 - 3^6 + 7^6 + 0^1 - 3^8$	$63761 := 6^3 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 1^0$	$63879 := -6^2 + 3^8 - 8^4 + 7^4 + 9^5$
$63706 := 6^3 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 6^6$	$63762 := -6^3 + 3^1 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 2^9$	$63894 := -6^1 + 3^5 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 4^6$
$63707 := 6^6 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 7^5$	$63762 := 6^3 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 2^1$	$63899 := -6^2 - 3^7 + 8^3 + 9^4 + 9^5$
$63708 := 6^6 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 0^0 + 8^0$	$63763 := 6^3 + 3^1 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 3^4$	$63924 := -6^4 - 3^5 - 9^1 - 2^6 + 4^8$
$63720 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 0^1$	$63764 := -6^1 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 4^3$	$63924 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 9^3 + 2^7 + 4^7$
$63721 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 1^0$	$63764 := 6^2 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 4^4$	$63925 := -6^5 + 3^2 - 9^4 + 2^7 + 5^7$
$63722 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^1 + 2^8$	$63765 := 6^3 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 5^1$	$63929 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 9^4 + 2^9 + 9^5$
$63723 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^4 + 3^5$	$63766 := 6^1 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^3 + 6^6$	$63942 := 6^2 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 2^5$
$63724 := -6^4 - 3^1 - 7^0 - 2^9 + 4^8$	$63767 := -6^2 - 3^1 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$63942 := -6^4 - 3^4 - 9^3 + 4^8 + 2^9$
$63724 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^2 + 4^4$	$63767 := 6^3 + 3^4 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$63943 := -6^3 + 3^4 - 9^3 + 4^8 - 3^6$
$63725 := -6^2 + 3^7 - 7^5 + 2^8 + 5^7$	$63768 := -6^3 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 8^3$	$63944 := 6^1 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 4^6$
$63725 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 5^1$	$63768 := 6^3 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 8^1$	$63944 := -6^3 - 3^2 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 4^6$
$63726 := 6^1 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 6^6$	$63769 := 6^3 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 9^2$	$63945 := -6^4 + 3^8 + 9^5 + 4^4 - 5^4$
$63726 := -6^1 - 3^5 + 7^5 + 2^9 + 6^6$	$63784 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 8^2 + 4^4$	$63946 := 6^2 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 6^2$
$63727 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 2^8 + 7^5$	$63786 := -6^3 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 6^6$	$63946 := -6^3 + 3^1 - 9^2 + 4^8 - 6^4$
$63728 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 8^1$	$63789 := -6^2 + 3^6 - 7^2 + 8^4 + 9^5$	$63947 := 6^3 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 7^3$
$63729 := -6^2 + 3^7 + 7^4 + 2^7 + 9^5$	$63824 := -6^2 - 3^7 - 8^0 + 2^9 + 4^8$	$63947 := -6^4 - 3^5 - 9^0 + 4^8 - 7^2$
$63729 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8 + 9^1$	$63834 := -6^2 + 3^5 - 8^4 + 3^7 + 4^8$	$63949 := -6^1 + 3^4 + 9^3 + 4^6 + 9^5$
$63734 := 6^6 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 4^0$	$63834 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 8^2 + 3^6 + 4^7$	$63967 := -6^3 - 3^2 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 7^5$
$63742 := -6^4 - 3^3 - 7^3 + 4^8 - 2^7$	$63839 := -6^2 + 3^0 + 8^4 + 3^6 + 9^5$	$63985 := 6^4 + 3^1 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 5^5$
$63742 := 6^6 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 2^5$	$63851 := -6^5 - 3^8 + 8^2 + 5^7 - 1^0$	$63985 := -6^4 - 3^7 - 9^4 - 8^4 + 5^7$
$63744 := 6^6 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 4^2 + 4^4$	$63852 := -6^5 - 3^8 - 8^2 + 5^7 + 2^7$	$63987 := 6^4 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 7^4$
$63745 := -6^1 - 3^2 - 7^4 + 4^8 + 5^4$	$63853 := -6^5 + 3^0 + 8^2 + 5^7 - 3^8$	$63987 := -6^4 + 3^7 + 9^5 + 8^4 - 7^2$
$63745 := 6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	$63854 := -6^1 - 3^7 + 8^3 - 5^0 + 4^8$	$63988 := -6^4 - 3^5 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 8^5$
$63746 := 6^2 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 4^1 + 6^6$	$63855 := -6^6 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 5^7 - 5^4$	$64023 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 0^1 + 2^9 - 3^6$
		$64026 := -6^3 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 2^0 - 6^4$
		$64035 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 0^0 + 3^6 + 5^6$
		$64043 := -6^5 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 3^7$

$64048 := -6^4 - 4^4 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 8^2$	$64232 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 3^0 - 2^3$	$64263 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^2 + 6^2 - 3^2$
$64072 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 7^3 - 2^9$	$64233 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^0 + 3^0 - 3^2$	$64264 := -6^2 - 4^1 + 2^6 - 6^4 + 4^8$
$64094 := -6^4 - 4^3 - 0^0 - 9^2 + 4^8$	$64234 := -6^2 - 4^5 + 2^0 - 3^5 + 4^8$	$64265 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 6^0 + 5^2$
$64112 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 1^0 + 1^0 - 2^7$	$64235 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 3^0 - 5^1$	$64266 := -6^1 + 4^7 - 2^6 + 6^4 + 6^6$
$64115 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 1^0 + 1^0 - 5^3$	$64236 := -6^1 + 4^8 + 2^0 + 3^0 - 6^4$	$64267 := 6^2 + 4^4 + 2^9 + 6^6 + 7^5$
$64159 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 1^0 + 5^0 - 9^2$	$64237 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^0 + 3^1 - 7^1$	$64267 := -6^2 + 4^8 - 2^7 + 6^4 - 7^4$
$64174 := -6^4 - 4^2 - 1^0 - 7^2 + 4^8$	$64238 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^1 + 3^0 - 8^0$	$64268 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^4 + 6^2 + 8^1$
$64178 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 7^0 - 8^2$	$64239 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 3^0 - 9^0$	$64269 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^1 + 6^2 - 9^1$
$64192 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 1^0 + 9^2 - 2^7$	$64240 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 2^0 + 4^8 + 0^1$	$64272 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 7^0 + 2^5$
$64195 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 1^0 + 9^2 - 5^3$	$64241 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 2^0 + 4^8 + 1^0$	$64273 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 7^1 + 3^3$
$64197 := 6^6 + 4^1 + 1^0 + 9^3 + 7^5$	$64242 := -6^1 - 4^5 - 2^3 + 4^8 - 2^8$	$64274 := -6^4 + 4^0 - 2^4 + 7^2 + 4^8$
$64203 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^6 + 0^1 + 3^3$	$64243 := -6^2 - 4^2 - 2^9 + 4^8 - 3^6$	$64276 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 7^0 + 6^2$
$64204 := -6^4 - 4^1 - 2^5 + 0^1 + 4^8$	$64244 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 2^0 + 4^1 + 4^8$	$64278 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^5 + 7^1 - 8^0$
$64206 := -6^2 + 4^8 + 2^0 + 0^0 - 6^4$	$64245 := -6^1 - 4^5 - 2^8 + 4^8 - 5^1$	$64279 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 7^2 - 9^1$
$64207 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^4 + 0^1 - 7^2$	$64246 := -6^1 + 4^1 + 2^3 + 4^8 - 6^4$	$64280 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 0^1$
$64208 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^5 + 0^0 - 8^0$	$64247 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 2^0 + 4^8 + 7^1$	$64281 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 1^0$
$64209 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^5 + 0^1 + 9^0$	$64247 := 6^6 + 4^2 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 7^5$	$64282 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^1 + 8^1 + 2^5$
$64210 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^5 + 1^0 + 0^0$	$64248 := -6^3 - 4^5 + 2^4 + 4^8 - 8^2$	$64283 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^3 + 8^1 + 3^3$
$64213 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 1^0 - 3^3$	$64249 := -6^1 - 4^5 - 2^8 + 4^8 - 9^0$	$64283 := 6^6 + 4^7 + 2^1 + 8^3 + 3^6$
$64215 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 1^0 - 5^2$	$64250 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 0^0$	$64284 := -6^2 - 4^5 - 2^7 - 8^2 + 4^8$
$64222 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^1 + 2^4 - 2^5$	$64252 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 5^1 + 2^3$	$64285 := -6^4 - 4^7 - 2^8 + 8^4 + 5^7$
$64223 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^1 + 2^3 - 3^3$	$64253 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 5^1 + 3^2$	$64286 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^1 + 8^1 + 6^2$
$64224 := -6^2 - 4^5 + 2^2 - 2^8 + 4^8$	$64254 := -6^4 + 4^0 + 2^3 + 5^1 + 4^8$	$64287 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^4 + 8^2 - 7^0$
$64224 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 2^5 + 2^7 + 4^7$	$64256 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^3 + 5^2 - 6^0$	$64288 := -6^3 - 4^5 - 2^3 + 8^5 + 8^5$
$64225 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^1 + 2^3 - 5^2$	$64257 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 5^2 - 7^1$	$64289 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^4 + 8^2 + 9^0$
$64226 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 2^4 + 2^3 - 6^4$	$64258 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^0 + 5^2 - 8^1$	$64289 := 6^6 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 8^3 + 9^3$
$64227 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^2 + 2^5 - 7^2$	$64260 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^4 + 6^2 + 0^1$	$64290 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^5 + 9^2 + 0^0$
$64228 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^3 + 2^2 - 8^1$	$64261 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^4 + 6^1 - 1^0$	$64293 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 9^2 - 3^3$
$64229 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^2 + 2^1 - 9^1$	$64262 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 2^1 + 6^2 - 2^4$	$64294 := -6^3 - 4^5 - 2^0 - 9^0 + 4^8$
		$64295 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 9^2 - 5^2$
		$64297 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 2^0 + 9^1 + 7^2$
		$64299 := -6^4 + 4^0 - 2^4 + 9^4 + 9^5$

$64302 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 3^1 + 0^0 + 2^6$	$64345 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 3^4 + 4^8 + 5^2$	$64394 := -6^2 - 4^5 - 3^0 - 9^2 + 4^8$
$64304 := -6^3 - 4^5 + 3^2 - 0^0 + 4^8$	$64346 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^6$	$64394 := 6^3 + 4^5 + 3^2 + 9^5 + 4^6$
$64308 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^1 + 0^0 + 8^2$	$64349 := -6^3 + 4^0 - 3^5 + 4^8 - 9^3$	$64395 := -6^3 - 4^5 + 3^8 + 9^5 + 5^2$
$64309 := -6^4 - 4^1 + 3^8 - 0^0 + 9^5$	$64352 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 3^0 + 5^4 - 2^9$	$64395 := 6^6 + 4^7 + 3^0 + 9^3 + 5^4$
$64313 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 3^2 + 1^0 + 3^4$	$64353 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 3^5 + 5^1 - 3^6$	$64396 := -6^1 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 9^2 - 6^4$
$64314 := -6^4 + 4^3 + 3^2 + 1^0 + 4^8$	$64354 := -6^1 - 4^5 - 3^3 - 5^3 + 4^8$	$64397 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^3 + 9^2 + 7^2$
$64316 := -6^1 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 1^0 - 6^4$	$64355 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 3^2 + 5^3 - 5^0$	$64399 := -6^4 + 4^1 + 3^4 + 9^4 + 9^5$
$64317 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^3 + 1^0 + 7^2$	$64356 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^4$	$64407 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 0^1 + 7^3$
$64319 := -6^4 + 4^1 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 9^5$	$64357 := -6^1 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 7^5$	$64422 := -6^3 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 2^1 + 2^7$
$64321 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 2^0 - 1^0$	$64358 := -6^3 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 5^5 - 8^4$	$64423 := -6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 2^1 - 3^4$
$64322 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 2^1 - 2^0$	$64359 := -6^1 + 4^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 9^5$	$64424 := -6^3 + 4^3 - 4^5 + 2^6 + 4^8$
$64323 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 3^4$	$64364 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 3^3 + 6^6 + 4^7$	$64425 := -6^3 - 4^5 + 4^8 + 2^2 + 5^3$
$64324 := -6^3 - 4^5 + 3^3 + 2^0 + 4^8$	$64365 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 3^0 + 6^0 + 5^3$	$64426 := -6^1 + 4^3 + 4^8 + 2^7 - 6^4$
$64326 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 2^2 + 6^0$	$64367 := -6^6 - 4^3 - 3^8 - 6^0 + 7^6$	$64427 := -6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 2^7 + 7^2$
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$64329 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 3^8 + 2^4 + 9^5$	$64370 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 7^2 + 0^1$	$64429 := -6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 + 2^2 - 9^2$
$64330 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 0^1$	$64371 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 7^2 + 1^0$	$64441 := -6^1 - 4^3 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 1^0$
$64331 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 1^0$	$64372 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^1 + 7^0 + 2^7$	$64442 := -6^1 + 4^3 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 2^7$
$64332 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^0 + 3^3 + 2^6$	$64373 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^1 + 7^2 + 3^4$	$64443 := -6^1 - 4^3 - 4^5 + 4^8 + 3^0$
$64333 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^1 + 3^2 + 3^4$	$64374 := -6^1 + 4^5 - 3^7 + 7^1 + 4^8$	$64444 := -6^2 - 4^2 - 4^2 - 4^5 + 4^8$
$64334 := -6^3 - 4^4 - 3^0 - 3^6 + 4^8$	$64375 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 5^3$	$64445 := -6^1 + 4^3 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 5^3$
$64334 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 4^7$	$64376 := -6^3 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 7^3 - 6^4$	$64445 := 6^6 + 4^4 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 5^3$
$64335 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 5^1$	$64377 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 7^1 + 7^2$	$64448 := -6^4 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 4^8 - 8^2$
$64336 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 6^1$	$64378 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 7^2 + 8^1$	$64449 := 6^3 + 4^3 + 4^5 + 4^6 + 9^5$
$64337 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 7^1$	$64379 := -6^4 + 4^2 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 9^5$	$64449 := -6^4 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 4^8 + 9^2$
$64337 := 6^6 + 4^3 + 3^4 + 3^6 + 7^5$	$64384 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 4^8$	$64450 := -6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 5^2 - 0^0$
$64338 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 8^1$	$64386 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 6^0$	$64452 := -6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 2^0$
$64339 := -6^4 + 4^2 + 3^2 + 3^8 + 9^5$	$64392 := 6^1 + 4^6 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 2^9$	$64456 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 4^8 + 5^0 + 6^3$
$64342 := -6^4 + 4^0 - 3^3 + 4^8 + 2^7$	$64393 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 3^2 + 9^2 + 3^4$	$64457 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 4^8 - 5^3 + 7^3$
		$64460 := -6^4 + 4^1 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 0^1$
		$64461 := -6^4 + 4^1 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 1^0$
		$64462 := -6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 6^2 - 2^3$

$64463 := -6^4 + 4^1 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 3^1$	$64502 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 0^0 + 2^8$	$64579 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 5^1 + 7^3 + 9^0$
$64464 := -6^4 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 4^8$	$64504 := -6^1 - 4^5 - 5^0 - 0^0 + 4^8$	$64593 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 5^5 + 9^0 + 3^7$
$64464 := 6^4 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 6^6 + 4^7$	$64520 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 5^2 + 2^8 - 0^0$	$64593 := 6^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 3^7$
$64465 := -6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 6^2 - 5^1$	$64522 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 5^2 + 2^0 + 2^8$	$64597 := 6^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 7^4$
$64465 := 6^4 + 4^1 + 4^7 + 6^6 + 5^3$	$64533 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 3^4 - 3^5$	$64597 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 5^5 + 9^0 + 7^4$
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$64467 := -6^2 + 4^2 + 4^5 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$64534 := -6^1 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 3^3 + 4^8$	$64624 := 6^4 + 4^4 + 6^6 + 2^5 + 4^7$
$64468 := -6^4 + 4^1 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$64534 := 6^6 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 3^8 + 4^6$	$64627 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 6^2 + 2^3 + 7^3$
$64469 := -6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 6^2 - 9^0$	$64535 := -6^3 + 4^3 - 5^6 + 3^7 + 5^7$	$64629 := -6^3 + 4^8 + 6^1 + 2^5 - 9^3$
$64470 := -6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 7^1 + 0^0$	$64536 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 5^0 + 3^4 + 6^3$	$64643 := -6^1 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 4^8 - 3^7$
$64474 := -6^2 - 4^0 - 4^5 - 7^0 + 4^8$	$64537 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 3^5 + 7^2$	$64643 := 6^4 + 4^3 + 6^6 + 4^7 + 3^5$
$64476 := -6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 + 7^0 - 6^0$	$64537 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 3^5 + 7^2$	$64645 := -6^3 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 4^8 + 5^4$
$64476 := -6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 7^0 + 6^0$	$64538 := -6^2 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 3^2 - 8^4$	$64648 := -6^4 + 4^4 + 6^3 + 4^8 - 8^2$
$64478 := -6^2 - 4^5 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 8^0$	$64539 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 3^5 + 9^2$	$64649 := -6^1 + 4^3 - 6^3 + 4^8 - 9^3$
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$64484 := -6^2 - 4^5 + 4^2 - 8^1 + 4^8$	$64553 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 5^5 - 3^7$	$64665 := -6^2 + 4^8 - 6^3 + 6^1 - 5^4$
$64485 := -6^2 - 4^4 + 4^7 + 8^5 + 5^6$	$64554 := -6^1 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 5^5 + 4^8$	$64666 := -6^1 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 6^3 - 6^4$
$64487 := 6^6 + 4^4 + 4^4 + 8^3 + 7^5$	$64555 := 6^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 5^6$	$64667 := -6^2 + 4^5 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 7^5$
$64487 := -6^7 - 4^3 + 4^8 + 8^6 + 7^5$	$64556 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 5^3 + 6^3$	$64668 := -6^2 + 4^4 + 6^6 + 6^7 - 8^6$
$64488 := -6^3 - 4^4 + 4^8 - 8^2 - 8^3$	$64557 := -6^2 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 5^2 - 7^3$	$64675 := -6^1 - 4^0 + 6^6 + 7^4 + 5^6$
$64489 := -6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 8^1 - 9^1$	$64558 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 5^0 + 5^5 - 8^4$	$64682 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 6^4 + 8^3 - 2^6$
$64493 := -6^4 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 9^1 + 3^5$	$64563 := -6^2 + 4^8 - 5^5 + 6^0 + 3^7$	$64684 := -6^2 - 4^5 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 4^8$
$64494 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 4^4 - 9^0 + 4^8$	$64572 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 7^3 - 2^4$	$64687 := 6^4 + 4^7 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 7^3$
$64495 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 4^5 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$64573 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 7^1 - 3^6$	$64695 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 6^0 + 9^0 - 5^4$
$64496 := -6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 9^1 - 6^0$	$64573 := 6^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 3^6$	$64698 := 6^4 + 4^4 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 8^4$
$64497 := 6^6 + 4^0 + 4^5 + 9^1 + 7^5$	$64574 := -6^4 - 4^1 - 5^1 + 7^3 + 4^8$	$64712 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 2^7$
$64498 := -6^1 - 4^5 + 4^8 - 9^1 + 8^0$	$64576 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 5^0 + 7^3 - 6^4$	$64722 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 7^3 + 2^0 - 2^8$
$64499 := 6^6 + 4^0 + 4^7 + 9^3 + 9^3$	$64577 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 5^0 + 7^3 - 7^1$	$64723 := -6^2 + 4^8 - 7^2 + 2^0 - 3^6$
	$64578 := -6^2 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^4$	$64730 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 0^1$
		$64731 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 1^0$
		$64732 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 7^1 + 3^5 + 2^8$

$64732 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 2^1$	$64776 := 6^4 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 7^5 + 6^6$	$64858 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 8^0 + 5^4 - 8^1$
$64733 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 7^1 + 3^5 + 3^5$	$64779 := -6^2 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 7^1 - 9^3$	$64864 := 6^4 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 6^6 + 4^7$
$64733 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^1 + 3^5$	$64792 := 6^4 + 4^6 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 2^3$	$64865 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 6^0 + 5^4$
$64734 := 6^6 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 4^5$	$64792 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 7^2 + 9^3 - 2^7$	$64869 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 6^2 + 9^2$
$64735 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 7^3 + 3^3 + 5^3$	$64793 := 6^4 + 4^6 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 3^2$	$64875 := -6^2 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 7^0 - 5^4$
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$64736 := 6^1 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 6^6$	$64795 := -6^2 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$64890 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 9^2 + 0^0$
$64737 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^1 + 3^5 + 7^5$	$64795 := 6^3 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 5^5$	$64904 := -6^4 - 4^3 + 9^3 - 0^0 + 4^8$
$64738 := 6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 8^1$	$64803 := -6^1 + 4^8 + 8^0 + 0^0 - 3^6$	$64905 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 9^0 + 0^0 - 5^4$
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$64752 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 7^0 + 5^0 + 2^9$	$64810 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 1^0 + 0^0$	$64933 := -6^2 + 4^8 + 9^2 + 3^4 - 3^6$
$64753 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 7^2 + 5^0 - 3^6$	$64822 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 2^4 - 2^1$	$64934 := 6^2 + 4^5 + 9^5 + 3^6 + 4^6$
$64757 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 7^2 + 5^3 + 7^3$	$64823 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 2^4 - 3^0$	$64935 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 3^2 + 5^3$
$64758 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 5^1 + 8^3$	$64824 := -6^3 - 4^2 - 8^3 + 2^5 + 4^8$	$64936 := -6^2 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 3^1 - 6^4$
$64760 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 0^1$	$64825 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 2^4 + 5^0$	$64937 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 3^1 + 7^3$
$64761 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 1^0$	$64832 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 3^4 + 2^9$	$64937 := 6^4 + 4^1 + 9^5 + 3^7 + 7^4$
$64762 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 2^1$	$64833 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 3^5 - 3^6$	$64938 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 9^2 + 3^0 - 8^3$
$64763 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 3^1$	$64834 := -6^2 - 4^0 + 8^2 - 3^6 + 4^8$	$64939 := -6^1 + 4^3 - 9^3 + 3^8 + 9^5$
$64764 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 4^1$	$64835 := -6^7 - 4^8 - 8^0 + 3^9 + 5^8$	$64943 := -6^4 + 4^0 + 9^3 + 4^8 - 3^3$
$64765 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 5^1$	$64836 := -6^3 + 4^8 - 8^3 + 3^3 + 6^0$	$64945 := -6^4 - 4^0 + 9^2 + 4^8 + 5^4$
$64766 := 6^1 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^4 + 6^6$	$64843 := -6^1 - 4^4 - 8^3 + 4^8 + 3^4$	$64953 := -6^1 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 5^3 + 3^3$
$64767 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$64845 := -6^1 + 4^1 - 8^2 + 4^8 - 5^4$	$64954 := -6^4 - 4^2 + 9^3 + 5^0 + 4^8$
$64768 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 8^1$	$64847 := -6^4 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 4^8 + 7^3$	$64956 := -6^4 - 4^6 - 9^0 + 5^7 - 6^5$
$64769 := 6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 9^1$	$64849 := -6^1 - 4^2 + 8^2 + 4^8 - 9^3$	$64958 := 6^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 8^3$
$64773 := -6^2 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 7^0 - 3^6$	$64856 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 8^1 + 5^4 - 6^0$	$64958 := -6^4 - 4^2 + 9^5 + 5^5 + 8^4$
$64775 := -6^2 + 4^8 - 7^0 + 7^4 - 5^5$	$64857 := -6^4 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 5^4 - 7^1$	$64962 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 6^0 - 2^3$
		$64963 := -6^4 + 4^0 - 9^2 + 6^6 + 3^9$
		$64964 := -6^4 - 4^1 + 9^3 - 6^0 + 4^8$
		$64965 := -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 6^0 - 5^1$

$$\begin{aligned} 64969 &:= -6^4 + 4^8 - 9^0 + 6^0 + 9^3 & 65243 &:= -6^3 + 5^1 - 2^0 + 4^8 - 3^4 & 65369 &:= -6^3 - 5^2 + 3^9 + 6^6 - 9^3 \\ 64970 &:= -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 0^1 & 65244 &:= -6^2 - 5^0 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 4^8 & 65384 &:= -6^1 - 5^0 - 3^4 - 8^2 + 4^8 \\ 64971 &:= -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 1^0 & 65246 &:= -6^2 + 5^0 - 2^8 + 4^8 + 6^0 & 65385 &:= -6^5 - 5^4 - 3^5 - 8^4 + 5^7 \\ 64972 &:= -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 2^1 & 65247 &:= -6^1 - 5^4 - 2^0 + 4^8 + 7^3 & 65387 &:= -6^2 + 5^7 + 3^2 + 8^4 - 7^5 \\ 64973 &:= -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 3^1 & 65248 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 - 2^8 + 4^8 - 8^0 & 65390 &:= -6^3 - 5^1 + 3^8 + 9^5 + 0^0 \\ 64974 &:= -6^3 - 4^1 + 9^0 - 7^3 + 4^8 & 65254 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 4^8 & 65392 &:= -6^3 - 5^0 + 3^8 + 9^5 - 2^0 \\ 64975 &:= -6^1 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 7^2 + 5^3 & 65259 &:= -6^2 + 5^5 - 2^2 + 5^5 + 9^5 & 65394 &:= -6^3 + 5^0 + 3^8 + 9^5 - 4^0 \\ 64976 &:= -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 6^1 & 65264 &:= -6^3 - 5^2 - 2^5 + 6^0 + 4^8 & 65394 &:= -6^3 - 5^0 + 3^8 + 9^5 + 4^0 \\ 64977 &:= -6^3 + 4^8 - 9^0 + 7^0 - 7^3 & 65274 &:= -6^1 - 5^0 - 2^8 + 7^0 + 4^8 & 65396 &:= -6^3 + 5^0 + 3^8 + 9^5 + 6^0 \\ 64978 &:= -6^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 7^0 + 8^1 & 65276 &:= 6^4 + 5^1 + 2^9 + 7^5 + 6^6 & 65398 &:= -6^3 + 5^1 + 3^8 + 9^5 - 8^0 \\ 64979 &:= -6^4 + 4^6 + 9^3 + 7^4 + 9^5 & 65276 &:= -6^4 + 5^5 - 2^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 & 65402 &:= -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 0^0 - 2^7 \\ 64984 &:= -6^3 - 4^4 - 9^2 + 8^0 + 4^8 & 65284 &:= -6^3 - 5^1 - 2^5 + 8^0 + 4^8 & 65403 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 - 0^0 - 3^0 \\ 64987 &:= -6^3 + 4^8 + 9^1 + 8^0 - 7^3 & 65293 &:= -6^2 - 5^2 - 2^8 + 9^5 + 3^8 & 65404 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 - 4^0 + 0^1 + 4^8 \\ 64988 &:= -6^2 + 4^8 - 9^0 + 8^0 - 8^3 & 65294 &:= -6^3 - 5^0 - 2^4 - 9^1 + 4^8 & 65405 &:= -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 0^0 - 5^3 \\ 64992 &:= -6^3 + 4^8 - 9^2 + 9^1 - 2^8 & 65295 &:= -6^1 + 5^5 + 2^1 + 9^5 + 5^5 & 65406 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 0^1 + 6^0 \\ 64994 &:= -6^4 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 9^3 + 4^8 & 65304 &:= -6^3 - 5^2 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 4^8 & 65407 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 7^0 \\ 64995 &:= -6^1 + 4^2 + 9^4 + 9^5 - 5^4 & 65324 &:= -6^1 + 5^1 - 3^5 + 2^5 + 4^8 & 65412 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 - 1^0 + 2^3 \\ 64996 &:= -6^2 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 9^1 + 6^3 & 65329 &:= -6^3 - 5^0 + 3^8 - 2^6 + 9^5 & 65413 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 - 1^0 + 3^2 \\ 64998 &:= -6^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 + 9^5 - 8^3 & 65341 &:= -6^3 - 5^1 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 1^0 & 65418 &:= -6^1 - 5^4 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 8^3 \\ 65042 &:= -6^1 + 5^2 - 0^0 + 4^8 - 2^9 & 65342 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 + 3^0 + 4^8 - 2^6 & 65419 &:= -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 1^0 - 9^2 \\ 65074 &:= -6^4 - 5^7 + 0^1 - 7^6 + 4^9 & 65343 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 3^4 & 65420 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 2^4 - 0^0 \\ 65094 &:= -6^4 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 9^3 + 4^8 & 65344 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 4^8 & 65422 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 2^0 + 2^4 \\ 65142 &:= -6^1 + 5^3 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 2^9 & 65345 &:= -6^3 + 5^0 - 3^0 + 4^8 + 5^2 & 65423 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 2^0 - 3^4 \\ 65147 &:= -6^3 - 5^3 + 1^0 + 4^8 - 7^2 & 65345 &:= -6^3 - 5^0 + 3^0 + 4^8 + 5^2 & 65424 &:= -6^3 - 5^2 + 4^0 + 2^7 + 4^8 \\ 65204 &:= -6^3 - 5^3 + 2^3 + 0^0 + 4^8 & 65346 &:= -6^1 + 5^1 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^3 & 65427 &:= -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 2^0 - 7^2 \\ 65234 &:= -6^2 - 5^0 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^8 & 65347 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 7^2 & 65431 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 3^3 - 1^0 \\ 65234 &:= 6^6 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^7 & 65348 &:= -6^1 + 5^3 - 3^5 + 4^8 - 8^2 & 65432 &:= -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 3^4 - 2^4 \\ 65240 &:= -6^2 - 5^1 - 2^8 + 4^8 + 0^0 & 65349 &:= -6^2 - 5^3 - 3^3 + 4^8 + 9^0 & 65433 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 3^2 - 3^4 \\ 65242 &:= -6^2 - 5^0 - 2^0 + 4^8 - 2^8 & 65364 &:= -6^1 - 5^4 + 3^5 + 6^3 + 4^8 & 65433 &:= 6^6 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 3^4 + 3^7 \\ & & & & 65434 &:= -6^1 - 5^1 - 4^3 - 3^3 + 4^8 \\ & & & & 65435 &:= -6^3 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 3^2 + 5^3 \\ & & & & 65436 &:= -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 3^3 - 6^2 \end{aligned}$$

$65437 := -6^1 - 5^1 + 4^8 - 3^4 - 7^1$	$65468 := -6^1 + 5^0 + 4^8 + 6^0 - 8^2$	$65524 := -6^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 - 2^2 + 4^8$
$65438 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	$65472 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 7^1 - 2^6$	$65525 := -6^2 - 5^6 + 5^5 - 2^6 + 5^7$
$65439 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 3^2 - 9^2$	$65473 := -6^1 - 5^1 + 4^8 - 7^2 - 3^1$	$65540 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 0^1$
$65440 := -6^1 - 5^2 - 4^3 + 4^8 - 0^0$	$65473 := 6^6 + 5^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 3^3$	$65541 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 1^0$
$65442 := -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^0 + 4^8 - 2^6$	$65474 := -6^1 + 5^0 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 4^8$	$65542 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 2^3$
$65443 := -6^1 - 5^1 - 4^0 + 4^8 - 3^4$	$65475 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 7^2 - 5^1$	$65543 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 3^2$
$65445 := -6^3 + 5^0 - 4^0 + 4^8 + 5^3$	$65476 := -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 7^1 - 6^2$	$65544 := -6^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 4^2 + 4^8$
$65445 := -6^3 - 5^0 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 5^3$	$65477 := -6^1 - 5^1 + 4^8 + 7^0 - 7^2$	$65545 := 6^1 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 4^8 + 5^0$
$65447 := -6^2 - 5^1 + 4^0 + 4^8 - 7^2$	$65478 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 7^1 - 8^2$	$65545 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 5^1$
$65447 := 6^6 + 5^1 + 4^0 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$65479 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 7^2 - 9^0$	$65546 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 6^1$
$65448 := -6^3 + 5^3 + 4^1 + 4^8 - 8^0$	$65482 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 8^0 - 2^4$	$65547 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 5^2 + 4^8 - 7^1$
$65449 := -6^1 + 5^0 - 4^0 + 4^8 - 9^2$	$65483 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 8^0 + 3^2$	$65548 := -6^1 + 5^0 + 5^2 + 4^8 - 8^1$
$65449 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^0 + 4^8 - 9^2$	$65484 := -6^2 - 5^0 - 4^2 + 8^0 + 4^8$	$65549 := 6^1 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 9^0$
$65450 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 0^1$	$65486 := -6^2 - 5^1 + 4^8 - 8^1 - 6^0$	$65549 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 9^1$
$65451 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 1^0$	$65487 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 8^0 - 7^2$	$65564 := -6^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 6^2 + 4^8$
$65452 := -6^1 + 5^2 + 4^8 + 5^2 - 2^7$	$65488 := -6^2 - 5^1 + 4^8 + 8^0 - 8^1$	$65569 := -6^1 - 5^4 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^5$
$65453 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 5^1 - 3^4$	$65489 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 8^0 - 9^1$	$65584 := -6^1 - 5^1 - 5^1 + 8^2 + 4^8$
$65454 := -6^2 - 5^1 - 4^2 - 5^2 + 4^8$	$65490 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 9^1 + 0^1$	$65604 := 6^1 + 5^2 + 6^2 + 0^0 + 4^8$
$65455 := -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 5^2 - 5^2$	$65491 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 9^1 + 1^0$	$65614 := 6^2 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 1^0 + 4^8$
$65456 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 6^1$	$65492 := -6^1 - 5^1 + 4^8 - 9^0 - 2^5$	$65624 := -6^2 - 5^1 + 6^0 + 2^7 + 4^8$
$65457 := -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 5^0 - 7^2$	$65493 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 9^1 - 3^3$	$65634 := 6^1 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 3^4 + 4^8$
$65458 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 8^1$	$65493 := 6^2 + 5^3 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 3^7$	$65634 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 6^3 - 3^4 + 4^8$
$65459 := -6^1 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 5^1 - 9^2$	$65494 := -6^2 - 5^0 - 4^1 - 9^0 + 4^8$	$65639 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 9^5$
$65460 := -6^2 - 5^1 + 4^8 - 6^2 + 0^0$	$65495 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 9^1 - 5^2$	$65642 := -6^1 + 5^4 - 6^0 + 4^8 - 2^9$
$65462 := -6^1 - 5^1 + 4^8 + 6^0 - 2^6$	$65496 := -6^1 + 5^0 + 4^8 + 9^0 - 6^2$	$65642 := 6^2 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 2^6$
$65464 := -6^1 - 5^0 - 4^3 - 6^0 + 4^8$	$65497 := -6^1 - 5^0 + 4^8 - 9^2 + 7^2$	$65647 := -6^1 + 5^3 - 6^0 + 4^8 - 7^1$
$65466 := -6^2 + 5^0 + 4^8 + 6^0 - 6^2$	$65498 := -6^1 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 9^0 - 8^1$	$65647 := 6^2 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 7^2$
$65467 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 - 6^0 - 7^1$	$65499 := -6^2 - 5^0 + 4^8 + 9^0 - 9^0$	$65648 := -6^1 + 5^3 + 6^0 + 4^8 - 8^1$
$65467 := 6^6 + 5^2 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 7^4$	$65504 := -6^1 - 5^0 - 5^2 + 0^1 + 4^8$	$65649 := 6^1 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 9^2$
		$65653 := -6^2 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 5^4 + 3^9$
		$65654 := -6^1 + 5^1 - 6^1 + 5^3 + 4^8$
		$65655 := -6^1 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 5^7 - 5^6$

$$\begin{aligned} 65658 &:= -6^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 5^7 + 8^5 & 65784 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 + 7^3 - 8^2 + 4^8 & 65948 &:= -6^3 + 5^3 - 9^1 + 4^8 + 8^3 \\ 65659 &:= -6^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 5^3 + 9^5 & 65785 &:= -6^5 - 5^3 - 7^3 - 8^4 + 5^7 & 65964 &:= 6^1 + 5^3 + 9^2 + 6^3 + 4^8 \\ 65674 &:= 6^1 + 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^0 + 4^8 & 65788 &:= -6^3 + 5^3 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 8^5 & 65983 &:= -6^5 + 5^7 - 9^4 + 8^1 + 3^7 \\ 65674 &:= -6^3 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 4^8 & 65824 &:= 6^1 + 5^2 + 8^0 + 2^8 + 4^8 & 65984 &:= -6^3 - 5^0 + 9^3 - 8^2 + 4^8 \\ 65676 &:= 6^5 + 5^5 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 6^6 & 65834 &:= -6^1 + 5^3 - 8^2 + 3^5 + 4^8 & 66042 &:= -6^1 + 6^0 - 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^9 \\ 65685 &:= -6^3 - 5^7 - 6^0 + 8^7 - 5^9 & 65838 &:= 6^3 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 3^4 + 8^5 & 66042 &:= -6^1 - 6^0 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^9 \\ 65693 &:= -6^1 + 5^3 - 6^2 + 9^5 + 3^8 & 65839 &:= 6^3 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 3^8 + 9^5 & 66043 &:= -6^1 - 6^3 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 3^6 \\ 65693 &:= 6^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 3^7 & 65842 &:= 6^3 + 5^2 + 8^0 + 4^8 + 2^6 & 66044 &:= 6^2 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 4^4 + 4^8 \\ 65694 &:= 6^2 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 4^8 & 65847 &:= -6^1 - 5^2 - 8^0 + 4^8 + 7^3 & 66048 &:= -6^1 + 6^1 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 8^3 \\ 65695 &:= -6^2 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 9^5 + 5^7 & 65854 &:= -6^3 + 5^5 - 8^6 + 5^8 - 4^8 & 66049 &:= 6^3 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 9^2 \\ 65704 &:= -6^1 + 5^3 + 7^2 + 0^1 + 4^8 & 65857 &:= -6^6 - 5^6 - 8^6 + 5^8 - 7^3 & 66049 &:= -6^3 - 6^0 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 9^3 \\ 65704 &:= 6^2 + 5^3 + 7^1 + 0^1 + 4^8 & 65858 &:= -6^2 - 5^7 - 8^1 - 5^9 + 8^7 & 66098 &:= -6^3 + 6^5 + 0^0 + 9^5 - 8^3 \\ 65724 &:= 6^1 + 5^1 + 7^2 + 2^7 + 4^8 & 65865 &:= -6^2 - 5^7 + 8^7 - 6^0 - 5^9 & 66123 &:= -6^3 + 6^6 - 1^0 + 2^0 + 3^9 \\ 65724 &:= -6^1 + 5^2 - 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^8 & 65874 &:= -6^6 + 5^0 - 8^4 + 7^6 - 4^5 & 66132 &:= -6^3 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 2^3 \\ 65742 &:= -6^1 + 5^1 - 7^2 + 4^8 + 2^8 & 65876 &:= -6^6 + 5^7 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 6^4 & 66133 &:= -6^3 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 3^2 + 3^9 \\ 65743 &:= 6^1 + 5^3 + 7^2 + 4^8 + 3^3 & 65877 &:= 6^6 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 7^4 + 7^5 & 66173 &:= -6^3 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 7^2 + 3^9 \\ 65743 &:= -6^1 - 5^0 + 7^4 + 4^8 - 3^7 & 65878 &:= -6^1 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 8^5 & 66194 &:= -6^2 - 6^2 + 1^0 + 9^3 + 4^8 \\ 65744 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 + 7^3 - 4^1 + 4^8 & 65878 &:= 6^3 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 8^5 & 66195 &:= -6^1 + 6^5 + 1^0 + 9^5 - 5^4 \\ 65746 &:= -6^1 + 5^0 - 7^0 + 4^8 + 6^3 & 65879 &:= 6^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 7^4 + 9^5 & 66224 &:= -6^2 + 6^3 - 2^2 + 2^9 + 4^8 \\ 65746 &:= -6^1 - 5^0 + 7^0 + 4^8 + 6^3 & 65894 &:= 6^3 + 5^3 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 4^8 & 66224 &:= 6^3 + 6^3 + 2^7 + 2^7 + 4^8 \\ 65747 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 - 7^0 + 4^8 + 7^3 & 65895 &:= -6^1 - 5^7 + 8^7 - 9^0 - 5^9 & 66234 &:= -6^2 + 6^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^8 \\ 65747 &:= 6^2 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 4^8 + 7^2 & 65924 &:= 6^1 + 5^3 + 9^0 + 2^8 + 4^8 & 66238 &:= -6^2 + 6^6 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 8^2 \\ 65748 &:= -6^1 + 5^4 - 7^3 + 4^8 - 8^2 & 65942 &:= 6^3 + 5^3 + 9^0 + 4^8 + 2^6 & 66242 &:= -6^1 + 6^3 - 2^4 + 4^8 + 2^9 \\ 65749 &:= 6^1 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 4^8 + 9^2 & 65942 &:= -6^3 + 5^4 - 9^0 + 4^8 - 2^1 & 66243 &:= -6^2 + 6^1 + 2^3 + 4^8 + 3^6 \\ 65749 &:= -6^1 - 5^3 + 7^3 + 4^8 + 9^0 & 65943 &:= -6^3 - 5^2 - 9^2 + 4^8 + 3^6 & 66243 &:= 6^3 + 6^3 + 2^5 + 4^8 + 3^5 \\ 65750 &:= 6^6 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 & 65944 &:= -6^4 - 5^0 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 4^6 & 66244 &:= -6^2 - 6^3 - 2^6 + 4^5 + 4^8 \\ 65764 &:= 6^1 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 6^3 + 4^8 & 65945 &:= -6^3 + 5^0 - 9^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 & 66245 &:= -6^1 - 6^5 - 2^1 - 4^6 + 5^7 \\ 65764 &:= -6^1 + 5^2 - 7^1 + 6^3 + 4^8 & 65945 &:= -6^3 - 5^0 + 9^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 & 66245 &:= 6^2 + 6^2 + 2^9 + 4^8 + 5^3 \\ 65783 &:= 6^6 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 3^7 & 65947 &:= -6^2 - 5^4 + 9^3 + 4^8 + 7^3 & 66247 &:= -6^4 + 6^6 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 7^5 \\ & & & & 66248 &:= 6^2 + 6^2 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 8^3 \\ & & & & 66249 &:= -6^1 - 6^1 - 2^2 + 4^8 + 9^3 \\ & & & & 66249 &:= 6^4 + 6^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 9^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66254 &:= -6^2 + 6^0 + 2^7 + 5^4 + 4^8 & 66344 &:= -6^3 + 6^0 - 3^0 + 4^5 + 4^8 & 66378 &:= 6^3 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 7^5 + 8^3 \\ 66258 &:= -6^5 + 6^0 + 2^2 + 5^7 - 8^4 & 66344 &:= -6^3 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 4^5 + 4^8 & 66379 &:= -6^1 + 6^5 + 3^2 + 7^6 - 9^5 \\ 66263 &:= -6^1 - 6^1 - 2^6 + 6^6 + 3^9 & 66345 &:= 6^6 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^0 & 66384 &:= 6^2 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 8^1 + 4^0 \\ 66264 &:= -6^1 + 6^1 + 2^9 + 6^3 + 4^8 & 66347 &:= 6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 7^0 & 66392 &:= 6^2 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 2^4 \\ 66294 &:= -6^1 + 6^2 - 2^0 + 9^3 + 4^8 & 66348 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 8^0 & 66392 &:= -6^2 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 2^3 \\ 66302 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 - 2^5 & 66350 &:= 6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 0^1 & 66393 &:= 6^2 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 9^1 + 3^9 \\ 66303 &:= -6^2 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 0^0 + 3^9 & 66351 &:= 6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 1^0 & 66393 &:= -6^2 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 9^2 + 3^9 \\ 66304 &:= -6^2 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 4^0 & 66352 &:= 6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 2^1 & 66394 &:= -6^1 + 6^3 - 3^4 + 9^3 + 4^8 \\ 66305 &:= -6^2 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 5^0 & 66353 &:= 6^1 + 6^6 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 3^9 & 66396 &:= -6^3 - 6^3 + 3^1 + 9^5 + 6^5 \\ 66312 &:= -6^2 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 2^3 & 66354 &:= 6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 4^1 & 66398 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 8^2 \\ 66313 &:= -6^2 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 1^0 + 3^9 & 66354 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 4^2 & 66423 &:= -6^1 + 6^2 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 3^6 \\ 66320 &:= -6^2 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 2^4 + 0^0 & 66355 &:= 6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 5^1 & 66423 &:= 6^2 + 6^6 + 4^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 \\ 66324 &:= -6^1 + 6^0 + 3^6 + 2^6 + 4^8 & 66356 &:= 6^1 + 6^1 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 6^6 & 66424 &:= -6^2 - 6^2 + 4^5 - 2^6 + 4^8 \\ 66326 &:= -6^1 - 6^1 + 3^9 - 2^0 + 6^6 & 66357 &:= 6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 7^1 & 66425 &:= 6^2 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 2^9 + 5^3 \\ 66327 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 2^0 - 7^1 & 66357 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 7^0 & 66427 &:= -6^3 - 6^4 + 4^8 + 2^1 + 7^4 \\ 66330 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 - 3^1 + 3^9 + 0^1 & 66358 &:= 6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 8^1 & 66428 &:= 6^2 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 8^3 \\ 66331 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 3^9 - 1^0 & 66359 &:= 6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^1 & 66432 &:= -6^2 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 2^7 \\ 66332 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^0 + 3^9 - 2^1 & 66359 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 9^0 & 66434 &:= -6^4 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 3^7 + 4^8 \\ 66333 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 - 3^0 + 3^0 + 3^9 & 66362 &:= 6^1 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 6^6 + 2^4 & 66442 &:= -6^1 + 6^4 - 4^4 + 4^8 - 2^7 \\ 66334 &:= 6^1 + 6^2 + 3^3 + 3^6 + 4^8 & 66362 &:= 6^1 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 6^6 + 2^4 & 66443 &:= 6^2 + 6^6 + 4^1 + 4^3 + 3^9 \\ 66334 &:= -6^1 - 6^1 + 3^4 + 3^6 + 4^8 & 66368 &:= -6^1 + 6^2 + 3^9 + 6^6 - 8^0 & 66443 &:= -6^3 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 4^4 + 3^9 \\ 66335 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^0 + 3^9 + 5^0 & 66372 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 2^5 & 66444 &:= -6^3 + 6^2 + 4^3 + 4^5 + 4^8 \\ 66336 &:= -6^1 + 6^1 - 3^1 + 3^9 + 6^6 & 66373 &:= 6^1 + 6^6 + 3^3 + 7^0 + 3^9 & 66445 &:= -6^1 + 6^4 - 4^4 + 4^8 - 5^3 \\ 66337 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^1 + 3^9 + 7^0 & 66373 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 - 3^2 + 7^2 + 3^9 & 66445 &:= 6^3 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 \\ 66338 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 - 3^1 + 3^9 + 8^1 & 66374 &:= 6^2 + 6^3 + 3^5 + 7^3 + 4^8 & 66449 &:= -6^2 + 6^1 + 4^5 + 4^8 - 9^2 \\ 66339 &:= -6^1 + 6^1 + 3^6 + 3^8 + 9^5 & 66374 &:= -6^2 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 4^3 & 66453 &:= -6^4 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 5^2 + 3^7 \\ 66342 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 2^3 & 66375 &:= -6^3 + 6^6 + 3^1 + 7^5 + 5^5 & 66454 &:= 6^2 + 6^0 + 4^4 + 5^4 + 4^8 \\ 66342 &:= 6^6 + 6^0 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 2^0 & 66376 &:= -6^1 - 6^1 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 6^6 & 66458 &:= -6^3 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 + 8^3 \\ 66343 &:= -6^1 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 4^0 + 3^9 & 66377 &:= 6^2 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 7^0 & 66459 &:= 6^3 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 + 9^2 \\ & & 66377 &:= -6^3 + 6^6 + 3^6 + 7^4 + 7^5 & 66464 &:= -6^3 - 6^3 + 4^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 \\ & & & & 66469 &:= -6^1 - 6^1 + 4^8 + 6^3 + 9^3 \\ & & & & 66474 &:= -6^2 - 6^0 + 4^5 - 7^2 + 4^8 \end{aligned}$$

$66480 := 6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 0^1$	$66594 := -6^3 + 6^5 + 5^0 + 9^5 - 4^2$	$66789 := -6^2 + 6^5 - 7^0 + 8^0 + 9^5$
$66481 := 6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 1^0$	$66597 := -6^3 + 6^5 - 5^1 + 9^5 - 7^1$	$66790 := -6^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 0^1$
$66482 := 6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 2^1$	$66599 := -6^3 + 6^5 - 5^0 + 9^5 - 9^1$	$66791 := -6^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 1^0$
$66483 := -6^1 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^1 + 3^6$	$66609 := -6^3 - 6^0 + 6^5 + 0^0 + 9^5$	$66792 := -6^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 2^1$
$66483 := 6^3 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 8^0 + 3^6$	$66614 := -6^3 - 6^0 + 6^4 - 1^0 + 4^8$	$66793 := -6^1 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 - 3^3$
$66484 := -6^1 - 6^1 + 4^5 - 8^2 + 4^8$	$66623 := 6^2 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 2^5 + 3^9$	$66794 := -6^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 4^1$
$66484 := 6^3 + 6^3 + 4^1 + 8^3 + 4^8$	$66624 := -6^3 + 6^1 + 6^4 + 2^1 + 4^8$	$66795 := -6^1 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 - 5^2$
$66485 := 6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 5^1$	$66632 := 6^2 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 2^8$	$66796 := -6^2 + 6^1 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 6^5$
$66486 := 6^1 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 6^3$	$66642 := -6^1 - 6^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 2^5$	$66797 := -6^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 7^1$
$66487 := 6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 7^1$	$66643 := -6^3 + 6^2 + 6^4 + 4^8 - 3^2$	$66799 := -6^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 9^5$
$66488 := -6^2 - 6^2 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 8^5$	$66644 := -6^2 - 6^3 + 6^4 + 4^3 + 4^8$	$66804 := -6^2 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 0^1 + 4^8$
$66488 := 6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^1 + 8^3$	$66646 := -6^1 + 6^2 - 6^3 + 4^8 + 6^4$	$66819 := -6^1 + 6^5 - 8^0 + 1^0 + 9^5$
$66489 := 6^3 + 6^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 9^1$	$66647 := 6^5 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 4^6 + 7^3$	$66823 := -6^2 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 2^9 + 3^9$
$66489 := -6^3 - 6^4 + 4^8 - 8^4 + 9^4$	$66649 := -6^3 + 6^2 + 6^5 + 4^1 + 9^5$	$66827 := -6^1 - 6^6 - 8^4 - 2^6 + 7^6$
$66532 := 6^2 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 2^5$	$66687 := -6^3 - 6^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 + 7^6$	$66828 := -6^1 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 8^5$
$66534 := 6^1 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 4^3$	$66689 := -6^2 - 6^2 + 6^5 - 8^2 + 9^5$	$66829 := -6^1 + 6^5 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 9^5$
$66534 := -6^2 + 6^6 - 5^2 + 3^9 + 4^4$	$66692 := -6^1 + 6^0 + 6^5 + 9^5 - 2^7$	$66829 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 9^5$
$66536 := 6^2 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 6^6$	$66695 := -6^1 + 6^0 + 6^5 + 9^5 - 5^3$	$66834 := -6^1 + 6^4 - 8^0 + 3^2 + 4^8$
$66539 := -6^1 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 9^2$	$66732 := 6^3 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 2^7$	$66840 := 6^1 + 6^4 + 8^0 + 4^8 + 0^0$
$66553 := -6^2 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 5^3 + 3^9$	$66734 := 6^2 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 4^2$	$66842 := -6^1 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 4^8 + 2^3$
$66554 := -6^1 - 6^2 - 5^6 + 5^7 + 4^6$	$66734 := -6^2 - 6^4 + 7^3 + 3^7 + 4^8$	$66842 := 6^4 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 4^8 + 2^3$
$66557 := -6^1 + 6^6 - 5^2 + 5^5 + 7^5$	$66737 := 6^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^9 + 7^3$	$66843 := -6^1 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 4^8 + 3^2$
$66559 := -6^2 + 6^4 + 5^5 + 5^5 + 9^5$	$66738 := -6^4 + 6^6 - 7^4 + 3^9 + 8^4$	$66843 := 6^4 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 4^8 + 3^2$
$66571 := -6^4 - 6^6 - 5^5 + 7^6 - 1^0$	$66739 := -6^3 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 3^8 + 9^5$	$66844 := -6^2 + 6^4 + 8^2 + 4^8 - 4^2$
$66573 := -6^1 + 6^6 + 5^5 + 7^5 - 3^2$	$66746 := -6^2 - 6^0 - 7^2 + 4^8 + 6^4$	$66847 := 6^1 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 4^8 + 7^0$
$66576 := -6^1 - 6^1 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 6^6$	$66748 := -6^2 + 6^4 - 7^2 + 4^8 + 8^0$	$66849 := 6^2 + 6^2 + 8^3 + 4^8 + 9^3$
$66592 := -6^3 + 6^5 - 5^0 + 9^5 - 2^4$	$66752 := 6^2 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 2^7$	$66853 := 6^6 + 6^0 + 8^3 + 5^0 + 3^9$
$66593 := -6^3 + 6^5 - 5^2 + 9^5 + 3^2$	$66759 := -6^4 - 6^5 + 7^5 - 5^2 + 9^5$	$66854 := -6^4 + 6^0 - 8^3 + 5^5 + 4^8$
$66594 := 6^3 + 6^3 + 5^4 + 9^0 + 4^8$	$66769 := -6^1 - 6^0 - 7^2 + 6^5 + 9^5$	$66858 := 6^4 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 5^2 + 8^5$
		$66859 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 5^2 + 9^5$
		$66863 := 6^1 + 6^1 + 8^3 + 6^6 + 3^9$

$66867 := -6^2 - 6^6 - 8^4 + 6^1 + 7^6$	$66937 := 6^2 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$67297 := 6^5 + 7^0 + 2^7 + 9^5 + 7^3$
$66874 := -6^1 + 6^4 - 8^0 + 7^2 + 4^8$	$66938 := 6^1 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 3^9 + 8^3$	$67298 := -6^5 - 7^5 + 2^6 + 9^5 + 8^5$
$66884 := 6^2 + 6^4 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 4^8$	$66939 := 6^1 + 6^4 + 9^4 + 3^3 + 9^5$	$67322 := 6^6 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 2^7 + 2^9$
$66887 := 6^1 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 7^2$	$66943 := 6^2 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^8$	$67325 := 6^6 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 2^3 + 5^5$
$66890 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 0^1$	$66945 := -6^1 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 5^3$	$67328 := -6^6 + 7^6 - 3^4 + 2^9 - 8^4$
$66891 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 1^0$	$66952 := -6^1 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 2^7$	$67342 := -6^1 - 7^3 + 3^7 + 4^8 - 2^5$
$66892 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 2^1$	$66952 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 2^0$	$67343 := 6^1 + 7^3 + 3^6 + 4^8 + 3^6$
$66893 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 3^1$	$66953 := -6^1 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 3^2$	$67343 := -6^2 - 7^3 - 3^0 + 4^8 + 3^7$
$66894 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 4^1$	$66953 := 6^4 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 5^5 + 3^7$	$67344 := 6^1 + 7^2 + 3^6 + 4^5 + 4^8$
$66895 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 5^1$	$66954 := 6^2 + 6^4 + 9^2 + 5^1 + 4^8$	$67345 := -6^2 - 7^3 + 3^7 + 4^8 + 5^0$
$66895 := -6^7 + 6^0 + 8^6 + 9^4 + 5^7$	$66957 := 6^1 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 7^0$	$67346 := -6^3 + 7^0 + 3^6 + 4^8 + 6^4$
$66896 := 6^1 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 6^5$	$66957 := -6^3 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 7^3$	$67348 := 6^4 + 7^0 + 3^1 + 4^8 + 8^3$
$66897 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 7^1$	$66974 := 6^2 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 4^3$	$67363 := -6^4 + 7^4 - 3^4 + 6^6 + 3^9$
$66897 := -6^6 - 6^0 - 8^4 + 9^0 + 7^6$	$66993 := 6^1 + 6^4 + 9^2 + 9^5 + 3^8$	$67364 := -6^1 + 7^1 + 3^9 + 6^6 + 4^5$
$66898 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 8^2$	$66994 := -6^1 + 6^1 + 9^3 + 9^3 + 4^8$	$67385 := -6^3 - 7^5 + 3^7 + 8^4 + 5^7$
$66899 := -6^1 + 6^4 - 8^0 + 9^4 + 9^5$	$66995 := -6^2 + 6^4 + 9^4 + 9^5 + 5^3$	$67389 := 6^5 + 7^2 + 3^1 + 8^3 + 9^5$
$66899 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^1 + 9^5$	$66995 := 6^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 5^3$	$67413 := 6^6 + 7^2 + 4^5 + 1^0 + 3^9$
$66905 := -6^5 + 6^1 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 5^6$	$66996 := -6^2 + 6^3 - 9^1 + 9^5 + 6^5$	$67415 := -6^4 + 7^2 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 5^5$
$66913 := 6^1 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 3^8$	$67024 := -6^6 + 7^6 - 0^0 + 2^7 - 4^6$	$67432 := -6^2 + 7^0 + 4^8 + 3^7 - 2^8$
$66915 := -6^2 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^3$	$67088 := -6^7 + 7^6 - 0^0 + 8^6 - 8^5$	$67432 := 6^4 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 2^9$
$66922 := 6^5 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 2^6$	$67144 := 6^6 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 4^6 + 4^7$	$67433 := -6^3 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 3^7 - 3^4$
$66923 := 6^4 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 2^4 + 3^8$	$67184 := 6^4 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 4^8$	$67434 := 6^4 + 7^3 + 4^2 + 3^5 + 4^8$
$66926 := 6^2 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 6^5$	$67234 := 6^4 + 7^3 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^8$	$67434 := -6^4 + 7^4 + 4^3 + 3^6 + 4^8$
$66932 := -6^1 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 3^8 + 2^5$	$67234 := -6^4 + 7^4 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^8$	$67435 := -6^1 + 7^3 + 4^8 + 3^7 - 5^4$
$66933 := -6^3 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 3^8$	$67235 := -6^5 - 7^4 + 2^4 - 3^6 + 5^7$	$67438 := -6^1 - 7^0 + 4^8 - 3^7 + 8^4$
$66934 := -6^1 + 6^4 + 9^2 + 3^3 + 4^8$	$67240 := 6^4 + 7^3 + 2^6 + 4^8 + 0^0$	$67452 := -6^4 + 7^3 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 2^8$
$66934 := 6^2 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$67255 := -6^5 - 7^0 + 2^5 - 5^5 + 5^7$	$67453 := -6^3 - 7^2 + 4^8 - 5^1 + 3^7$
$66935 := -6^5 + 6^2 + 9^5 + 3^0 + 5^6$	$67295 := 6^5 + 7^3 + 2^1 + 9^5 + 5^3$	$67458 := -6^3 + 7^6 - 4^8 + 5^6 - 8^2$
$66936 := -6^1 + 6^2 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 6^5$	$67296 := -6^4 + 7^5 + 2^9 + 9^5 - 6^5$	$67459 := 6^4 + 7^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 + 9^0$
		$67465 := 6^4 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 6^0 + 5^4$
		$67472 := -6^3 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 7^4 - 2^8$
		$67475 := -6^4 - 7^6 + 4^9 + 7^4 - 5^7$

$67480 := 6^6 + 7^3 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 0^0$	$67729 := -6^5 - 7^3 + 7^5 - 2^3 + 9^5$	$67923 := 6^5 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 2^9 + 3^5$
$67493 := 6^6 + 7^2 + 4^5 + 9^2 + 3^9$	$67743 := 6^1 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 3^7$	$67924 := -6^1 + 7^4 - 9^1 + 2^1 + 4^8$
$67495 := -6^4 + 7^2 + 4^8 + 9^2 + 5^5$	$67743 := -6^2 + 7^1 + 7^2 + 4^8 + 3^7$	$67925 := -6^5 - 7^4 + 9^1 - 2^5 + 5^7$
$67524 := -6^3 + 7^6 + 5^6 + 2^1 - 4^8$	$67744 := -6^3 + 7^1 + 7^4 + 4^2 + 4^8$	$67927 := -6^6 - 7^4 - 9^3 + 2^6 + 7^6$
$67527 := -6^6 - 7^3 - 5^5 + 2^1 + 7^6$	$67745 := -6^3 - 7^0 + 7^4 + 4^8 + 5^2$	$67929 := 6^5 + 7^3 + 9^3 + 2^5 + 9^5$
$67542 := -6^4 + 7^2 + 5^5 + 4^8 + 2^7$	$67746 := -6^4 + 7^4 + 7^4 + 4^8 - 6^4$	$67940 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 0^1$
$67543 := -6^1 - 7^2 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 3^7$	$67764 := -6^3 + 7^1 + 7^4 + 6^2 + 4^8$	$67941 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 1^0$
$67543 := 6^4 + 7^3 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 3^5$	$67782 := -6^2 - 7^5 + 7^6 - 8^5 - 2^8$	$67942 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 2^1$
$67547 := -6^3 - 7^2 - 5^3 + 4^8 + 7^4$	$67784 := -6^3 - 7^0 + 7^4 + 8^2 + 4^8$	$67943 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 3^1$
$67549 := 6^5 + 7^3 + 5^3 + 4^4 + 9^5$	$67803 := 6^6 + 7^5 + 8^4 + 0^0 + 3^5$	$67944 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 4^8$
$67563 := -6^6 + 7^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 3^8$	$67805 := -6^6 + 7^6 - 8^2 + 0^0 - 5^5$	$67944 := 6^4 + 7^1 + 9^2 + 4^5 + 4^8$
$67568 := -6^6 + 7^6 - 5^4 + 6^4 - 8^4$	$67834 := -6^3 + 7^2 - 8^4 + 3^8 + 4^8$	$67945 := 6^1 + 7^4 + 9^0 + 4^8 + 5^0$
$67585 := 6^6 + 7^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 + 5^2$	$67835 := -6^2 - 7^5 - 8^1 + 3^8 + 5^7$	$67945 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 5^1$
$67624 := 6^6 + 7^5 + 6^0 + 2^6 + 4^6$	$67837 := -6^6 - 7^4 - 8^3 - 3^5 + 7^6$	$67946 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 6^1$
$67634 := 6^1 + 7^4 + 6^6 + 3^7 + 4^7$	$67845 := -6^3 + 7^4 - 8^0 + 4^8 + 5^3$	$67947 := -6^1 + 7^1 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 7^4$
$67634 := -6^1 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 3^4 + 4^6$	$67849 := -6^1 + 7^4 - 8^0 + 4^8 - 9^2$	$67947 := 6^5 + 7^2 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 7^2$
$67636 := -6^1 + 7^1 + 6^4 + 3^9 + 6^6$	$67852 := -6^5 - 7^4 - 8^2 + 5^7 - 2^5$	$67948 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 8^1$
$67637 := 6^4 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 7^0$	$67853 := -6^3 - 7^1 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 3^9$	$67949 := -6^1 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 9^1$
$67639 := 6^2 + 7^2 + 6^5 + 3^6 + 9^5$	$67854 := -6^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 5^3 + 4^8$	$67950 := -6^5 - 7^4 + 9^0 + 5^7 + 0^0$
$67643 := 6^4 + 7^1 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 3^9$	$67857 := -6^3 - 7^5 - 8^5 - 5^0 + 7^6$	$67956 := -6^5 - 7^4 + 9^1 + 5^7 - 6^0$
$67644 := -6^2 + 7^4 - 6^0 + 4^8 - 4^4$	$67859 := -6^4 - 7^4 - 8^1 + 5^7 - 9^4$	$67958 := -6^5 - 7^4 + 9^1 + 5^7 + 8^0$
$67649 := -6^5 - 7^1 - 6^0 + 4^7 + 9^5$	$67874 := -6^1 + 7^1 - 8^2 + 7^4 + 4^8$	$67962 := -6^4 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 2^5$
$67652 := -6^5 - 7^4 + 6^3 + 5^7 - 2^9$	$67875 := -6^6 - 7^0 + 8^1 + 7^6 - 5^5$	$67965 := 6^4 + 7^5 + 9^2 + 6^6 + 5^5$
$67672 := 6^4 + 7^4 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 2^9$	$67885 := -6^5 - 7^4 + 8^0 - 8^2 + 5^7$	$67966 := -6^4 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 6^5$
$67685 := 6^6 + 7^5 + 6^0 + 8^4 + 5^3$	$67894 := -6^2 + 7^4 - 8^1 + 9^0 + 4^8$	$67983 := -6^2 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 8^1 + 3^8$
$67693 := 6^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 3^9$	$67896 := 6^3 + 7^3 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 6^5$	$67984 := 6^4 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 4^7$
$67694 := -6^2 + 7^4 - 6^3 + 9^1 + 4^8$	$67898 := 6^5 + 7^2 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 8^3$	$67984 := -6^4 - 7^3 - 9^1 + 8^4 + 4^8$
$67724 := -6^2 - 7^2 + 7^4 - 2^7 + 4^8$	$67904 := 6^4 + 7^3 + 9^3 + 0^1 + 4^8$	$67987 := -6^1 - 7^5 - 9^2 - 8^5 + 7^6$
$67729 := 6^5 + 7^2 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 9^5$	$67923 := -6^3 + 7^4 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 3^8$	$67998 := -6^4 + 7^5 - 9^4 + 9^5 - 8^0$
		$68072 := 6^6 + 8^4 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 2^9$
		$68079 := -6^5 - 8^0 + 0^1 + 7^5 + 9^5$
		$68153 := -6^5 - 8^1 - 1^0 + 5^7 - 3^7$

$68224 := -6^4 + 8^4 - 2^7 + 2^4 + 4^8$	$68576 := -6^1 - 8^3 + 5^7 - 7^5 + 6^5$	$68844 := -6^4 + 8^3 + 8^4 + 4^8 - 4^1$
$68243 := 6^1 + 8^3 + 2^1 + 4^8 + 3^7$	$68597 := -6^5 + 8^3 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 7^5$	$68845 := -6^6 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 5^7$
$68264 := 6^4 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 6^4 + 4^8$	$68640 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 0^1$	$68847 := -6^4 + 8^3 + 8^4 + 4^8 - 7^0$
$68334 := -6^4 + 8^4 - 3^1 + 3^0 + 4^8$	$68641 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 1^0$	$68848 := -6^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 8^5$
$68340 := -6^4 + 8^4 + 3^1 + 4^8 + 0^0$	$68642 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 2^1$	$68849 := -6^4 + 8^3 + 8^4 + 4^8 + 9^0$
$68344 := -6^4 - 8^0 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 4^8$	$68643 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 3^1$	$68885 := 6^3 + 8^1 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 5^5$
$68346 := -6^4 + 8^4 + 3^2 + 4^8 + 6^0$	$68644 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^1 + 4^8$	$68934 := -6^3 - 8^4 + 9^5 - 3^7 + 4^7$
$68354 := -6^1 + 8^3 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 4^8$	$68645 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 5^1$	$68958 := 6^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 8^5$
$68359 := -6^4 - 8^4 + 3^7 + 5^7 - 9^4$	$68646 := 6^1 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 6^4$	$68959 := 6^3 + 8^1 + 9^4 + 5^5 + 9^5$
$68364 := -6^4 + 8^4 + 3^3 + 6^0 + 4^8$	$68647 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 7^1$	$68967 := -6^4 - 8^0 - 9^3 - 6^6 + 7^6$
$68374 := -6^6 + 8^5 - 3^4 + 7^5 + 4^8$	$68648 := 6^4 + 8^1 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 8^3$	$68976 := -6^4 + 8^1 - 9^3 + 7^6 - 6^6$
$68394 := -6^4 + 8^4 + 3^8 + 9^5 - 4^2$	$68649 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 9^1$	$68976 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 6^5$
$68424 := -6^3 + 8^4 - 4^5 + 2^5 + 4^8$	$68649 := -6^4 - 8^4 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 9^3$	$69013 := 6^5 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 1^0 + 3^7$
$68425 := -6^4 + 8^4 + 4^8 + 2^6 + 5^2$	$68669 := 6^2 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 6^5 + 9^5$	$69055 := -6^1 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 5^7 - 5^6$
$68427 := -6^1 - 8^5 - 4^7 - 2^6 + 7^6$	$68674 := -6^4 + 8^0 - 6^6 + 7^6 - 4^5$	$69064 := -6^5 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 6^7 - 4^9$
$68435 := -6^3 - 8^0 + 4^8 - 3^2 + 5^5$	$68733 := -6^6 - 8^2 + 7^6 - 3^2 - 3^7$	$69079 := -6^3 - 9^4 + 0^1 + 7^5 + 9^5$
$68445 := -6^3 + 8^0 - 4^0 + 4^8 + 5^5$	$68734 := -6^1 - 8^5 + 7^6 + 3^5 - 4^7$	$69093 := 6^4 + 9^4 + 0^1 + 9^5 + 3^7$
$68445 := -6^3 - 8^0 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 5^5$	$68735 := -6^5 - 8^4 + 7^4 + 3^4 + 5^7$	$69146 := 6^4 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 4^5 + 6^5$
$68447 := -6^1 + 8^3 + 4^1 + 4^8 + 7^4$	$68736 := -6^1 - 8^2 + 7^6 - 3^7 - 6^6$	$69234 := -6^3 + 9^5 - 2^8 + 3^8 + 4^6$
$68449 := 6^4 + 8^3 + 4^5 + 4^8 + 9^2$	$68737 := -6^6 + 8^2 - 7^4 + 3^4 + 7^6$	$69236 := 6^3 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 6^5$
$68452 := -6^3 - 8^0 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 2^3$	$68739 := 6^3 + 8^3 + 7^4 + 3^8 + 9^5$	$69237 := 6^5 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 7^4$
$68453 := -6^3 - 8^0 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 3^2$	$68743 := -6^6 - 8^2 + 7^6 + 4^0 - 3^7$	$69237 := -6^6 - 9^2 + 2^9 - 3^7 + 7^6$
$68454 := -6^3 + 8^1 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 4^8$	$68744 := -6^3 - 8^0 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 4^8$	$69245 := -6^4 - 9^4 + 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^7$
$68467 := -6^2 - 8^5 - 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^6$	$68753 := 6^6 + 8^1 + 7^4 + 5^1 + 3^9$	$69253 := 6^1 + 9^5 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 3^8$
$68534 := -6^2 - 8^2 + 5^5 - 3^3 + 4^8$	$68754 := 6^2 + 8^1 + 7^2 + 5^5 + 4^8$	$69273 := -6^1 + 9^5 - 2^4 + 7^5 - 3^8$
$68543 := -6^2 - 8^0 + 5^5 + 4^8 - 3^4$	$68777 := -6^1 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 7^5 + 7^5$	$69274 := 6^4 + 9^1 + 2^5 + 7^4 + 4^8$
$68557 := -6^6 + 8^2 - 5^5 + 5^4 + 7^6$	$68777 := 6^6 + 8^3 + 7^4 + 7^4 + 7^5$	$69275 := -6^5 - 9^3 - 2^1 - 7^3 + 5^7$
$68573 := -6^4 - 8^4 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 3^8$	$68797 := -6^1 - 8^5 - 7^5 + 9^3 + 7^6$	$69277 := 6^5 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 7^2 + 7^4$
$68574 := 6^6 + 8^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 + 4^7$	$68825 := 6^2 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 2^7 + 5^5$	$69279 := -6^6 - 9^3 - 2^8 + 7^6 - 9^3$
		$69297 := -6^1 - 9^4 + 2^3 + 9^5 + 7^5$
		$69307 := 6^4 + 9^5 + 3^8 + 0^1 + 7^4$
		$69325 := -6^2 - 9^4 - 3^7 - 2^4 + 5^7$

$69327 := -6^6 + 9^1 - 3^7 + 2^9 + 7^6$	$69479 := -6^3 - 9^0 + 4^8 - 7^4 + 9^4$	$69634 := 6^1 + 9^4 + 6^6 + 3^3 + 4^7$
$69343 := 6^4 + 9^2 + 3^5 + 4^8 + 3^7$	$69489 := -6^3 + 9^4 - 4^0 + 8^4 + 9^5$	$69634 := -6^2 + 9^5 - 6^2 + 3^8 + 4^6$
$69343 := -6^4 - 9^3 - 3^6 + 4^8 + 3^8$	$69490 := -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 0^1$	$69635 := -6^4 + 9^5 - 6^5 + 3^9 - 5^2$
$69344 := -6^2 - 9^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 4^8$	$69491 := -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 1^0$	$69648 := 6^1 + 9^1 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 8^4$
$69345 := -6^1 - 9^5 - 3^4 - 4^9 + 5^8$	$69492 := -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 2^1$	$69652 := -6^5 - 9^3 + 6^2 + 5^7 - 2^2$
$69347 := -6^5 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 4^5 + 7^5$	$69493 := -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 3^1$	$69653 := -6^3 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 5^5 - 3^4$
$69348 := -6^2 + 9^5 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 8^3$	$69494 := -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 9^5 + 4^6$	$69655 := -6^5 - 9^3 + 6^2 - 5^0 + 5^7$
$69349 := 6^4 + 9^4 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 9^5$	$69495 := -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 5^1$	$69657 := -6^5 - 9^3 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 7^0$
$69362 := 6^4 + 9^5 + 3^6 + 6^5 + 2^9$	$69496 := -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 6^1$	$69672 := -6^4 - 9^1 - 6^6 + 7^6 - 2^4$
$69365 := -6^1 - 9^4 - 3^7 - 6^1 + 5^7$	$69497 := -6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 7^1$	$69674 := -6^4 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 7^2 + 4^6$
$69367 := -6^5 + 9^5 - 3^2 + 6^4 + 7^5$	$69498 := -6^3 + 9^0 + 4^8 + 9^2 + 8^4$	$69675 := -6^5 - 9^3 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 5^7$
$69384 := -6^1 + 9^0 - 3^5 + 8^4 + 4^8$	$69499 := -6^3 + 9^1 + 4^6 + 9^4 + 9^5$	$69679 := -6^4 - 9^1 - 6^6 + 7^6 - 9^1$
$69385 := -6^5 - 9^3 - 3^5 + 8^1 + 5^7$	$69523 := -6^4 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 2^4 - 3^8$	$69685 := -6^5 - 9^3 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 5^7$
$69408 := -6^3 - 9^1 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 8^4$	$69524 := 6^1 + 9^3 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 4^8$	$69687 := -6^4 - 9^1 - 6^6 - 8^0 + 7^6$
$69414 := -6^3 - 9^0 + 4^6 - 1^0 + 4^8$	$69524 := -6^2 - 9^5 + 5^8 + 2^7 - 4^9$	$69694 := -6^1 + 9^4 - 6^1 + 9^5 + 4^6$
$69418 := -6^3 + 9^0 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 8^4$	$69538 := -6^4 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 3^8 - 8^0$	$69695 := -6^1 - 9^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 + 5^7$
$69425 := -6^1 - 9^5 - 4^9 - 2^0 + 5^8$	$69543 := -6^3 + 9^5 + 5^5 + 4^5 + 3^8$	$69697 := -6^4 - 9^0 - 6^6 + 9^0 + 7^6$
$69434 := 6^1 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 3^7 + 4^6$	$69544 := -6^1 - 9^2 - 5^0 + 4^6 + 4^8$	$69706 := -6^4 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 0^1 - 6^6$
$69434 := -6^2 - 9^2 + 4^6 - 3^4 + 4^8$	$69548 := -6^5 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 4^3 - 8^1$	$69724 := -6^2 + 9^4 - 7^4 + 2^6 + 4^8$
$69435 := -6^1 - 9^4 + 4^3 - 3^7 + 5^7$	$69562 := -6^5 - 9^3 + 5^7 + 6^1 - 2^6$	$69742 := 6^5 + 9^5 + 7^4 + 4^1 + 2^9$
$69435 := 6^2 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 3^6 + 5^5$	$69564 := -6^2 + 9^4 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 4^7$	$69743 := 6^2 + 9^5 + 7^0 + 4^6 + 3^8$
$69452 := -6^5 - 9^0 - 4^5 + 5^7 + 2^7$	$69567 := 6^3 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$69743 := -6^3 + 9^4 + 7^2 + 4^8 - 3^7$
$69453 := -6^1 - 9^5 - 4^9 + 5^8 + 3^3$	$69570 := -6^5 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 0^0$	$69746 := -6^3 + 9^3 + 7^4 + 4^8 + 6^4$
$69453 := 6^2 + 9^3 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 3^3$	$69572 := -6^5 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 7^2 + 2^0$	$69748 := -6^6 - 9^3 + 7^6 - 4^1 - 8^3$
$69473 := 6^5 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 3^5$	$69583 := -6^5 - 9^3 + 5^7 - 8^2 + 3^3$	$69749 := -6^1 + 9^4 + 7^2 + 4^6 + 9^5$
$69474 := -6^3 + 9^1 + 4^6 + 7^2 + 4^8$	$69615 := -6^1 - 9^3 - 6^5 + 1^0 + 5^7$	$69749 := 6^2 + 9^4 + 7^1 + 4^6 + 9^5$
$69475 := -6^1 - 9^5 - 4^9 + 7^2 + 5^8$	$69617 := -6^4 - 9^2 - 6^6 + 1^0 + 7^6$	$69762 := -6^1 + 9^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 - 2^8$
$69475 := 6^2 + 9^3 + 4^8 + 7^2 + 5^5$	$69625 := -6^5 - 9^3 + 6^0 + 2^2 + 5^7$	$69769 := -6^4 - 9^1 + 7^6 - 6^6 + 9^2$
$69476 := -6^1 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 6^5$	$69633 := -6^4 + 9^5 - 6^5 + 3^9 - 3^3$	$69785 := -6^2 - 9^5 - 7^6 + 8^6 - 5^6$
		$69786 := -6^4 + 9^2 + 7^6 + 8^1 - 6^6$
		$69787 := 6^5 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 8^3 + 7^4$
		$69835 := -6^5 - 9^0 - 8^3 - 3^0 + 5^7$

$69843 := -6^5 + 9^5 - 8^0 + 4^7 + 3^7$	$72043 := -7^2 - 2^2 - 0^0 + 4^8 + 3^8$	$72443 := 7^3 + 2^1 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 3^8$
$69852 := -6^5 - 9^0 - 8^3 + 5^7 + 2^4$	$72049 := -7^2 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 9^4$	$72449 := 7^3 + 2^3 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 9^4$
$69853 := -6^2 - 9^4 + 8^3 + 5^7 - 3^7$	$72094 := -7^1 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 9^4 + 4^8$	$72453 := -7^1 - 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^7 - 3^8$
$69854 := 6^3 + 9^0 + 8^4 + 5^1 + 4^8$	$72149 := 7^2 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 4^8 + 9^4$	$72453 := 7^3 + 2^3 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 3^8$
$69854 := -6^5 + 9^0 - 8^3 + 5^7 + 4^2$	$72234 := 7^1 + 2^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^8$	$72455 := -7^4 - 2^7 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 5^7$
$69895 := -6^5 - 9^5 - 8^4 + 9^6 - 5^8$	$72234 := -7^1 + 2^4 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^8$	$72456 := -7^3 - 2^9 + 4^8 - 5^0 + 6^5$
$69924 := 6^3 + 9^4 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^6$	$72259 := -7^4 + 2^1 - 2^4 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$72459 := -7^1 - 2^8 + 4^8 + 5^4 + 9^4$
$69927 := -6^6 - 9^2 - 9^3 - 2^8 + 7^6$	$72304 := -7^2 + 2^8 + 3^8 + 0^1 + 4^8$	$72473 := 7^3 + 2^5 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 3^8$
$69943 := -6^1 + 9^4 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 3^5$	$72325 := -7^1 + 2^8 - 3^8 + 2^9 + 5^7$	$72479 := 7^1 + 2^5 + 4^8 + 7^3 + 9^4$
$69945 := -6^3 - 9^5 + 9^3 - 4^9 + 5^8$	$72334 := -7^1 + 2^0 + 3^5 + 3^8 + 4^8$	$72493 := -7^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 9^5 - 3^3$
$69952 := 6^5 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 5^5 + 2^0$	$72342 := -7^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^8 + 2^8$	$72495 := -7^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 9^5 - 5^2$
$69965 := 6^1 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 5^5$	$72343 := -7^1 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^8 + 3^8$	$72497 := -7^1 + 2^6 + 4^8 + 9^4 + 7^3$
$69967 := -6^3 - 9^2 - 9^3 - 6^6 + 7^6$	$72343 := 7^4 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^8 + 3^7$	$72497 := 7^2 + 2^3 + 4^8 + 9^4 + 7^3$
$70347 := 7^4 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 4^8 + 7^4$	$72344 := -7^1 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 4^8$	$72499 := -7^3 + 2^4 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 9^4$
$70367 := 7^3 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 6^6 + 7^5$	$72345 := -7^1 + 2^8 + 3^8 + 4^8 - 5^0$	$72529 := -7^4 + 2^7 + 5^6 + 2^7 + 9^5$
$70386 := -7^2 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 6^6$	$72347 := -7^1 + 2^8 + 3^8 + 4^8 + 7^0$	$72543 := -7^2 + 2^2 + 5^7 + 4^5 - 3^8$
$70478 := 7^5 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 8^5$	$72349 := 7^1 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^8 + 9^4$	$72549 := -7^1 - 2^5 + 5^7 + 4^5 - 9^4$
$70488 := 7^3 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 8^4$	$72349 := -7^1 + 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^8 + 9^4$	$72687 := -7^4 - 2^0 - 6^6 + 8^4 + 7^6$
$70595 := -7^3 - 0^0 - 5^4 - 9^4 + 5^7$	$72355 := -7^4 - 2^0 - 3^5 - 5^5 + 5^7$	$72694 := 7^2 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^4 + 4^8$
$70675 := -7^3 + 0^1 - 6^6 + 7^6 + 5^2$	$72358 := -7^4 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 5^7 - 8^4$	$72747 := 7^4 + 2^3 + 7^4 + 4^8 + 7^4$
$70685 := 7^5 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 8^4 + 5^5$	$72364 := 7^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 4^8$	$72855 := -7^4 - 2^8 + 8^3 - 5^5 + 5^7$
$70846 := -7^4 - 0^0 - 8^2 + 4^8 + 6^5$	$72383 := -7^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^5 + 3^9$	$72875 := -7^4 - 2^9 + 8^2 - 7^4 + 5^7$
$70855 := -7^2 + 0^1 - 8^4 - 5^5 + 5^7$	$72385 := 7^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 8^5 + 5^5$	$72879 := -7^4 - 2^6 - 8^3 + 7^5 + 9^5$
$70976 := -7^1 - 0^0 - 9^1 + 7^6 - 6^6$	$72403 := 7^2 + 2^8 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 3^8$	$72896 := -7^2 + 2^3 - 8^5 + 9^5 + 6^6$
$71243 := -7^3 + 1^0 - 2^9 + 4^8 + 3^8$	$72432 := -7^2 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 3^8 + 2^8$	$72904 := -7^4 - 2^7 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 4^7$
$71513 := -7^2 - 1^0 + 5^7 - 1^0 - 3^8$	$72434 := 7^2 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 3^8 + 4^8$	$72927 := -7^4 - 2^4 + 9^5 - 2^9 + 7^5$
$71553 := -7^1 + 1^0 - 5^1 + 5^7 - 3^8$	$72435 := -7^2 + 2^9 + 4^8 + 3^8 - 5^3$	$72943 := -7^4 - 2^3 + 9^5 + 4^7 - 3^4$
$71559 := -7^1 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 5^7 - 9^4$	$72437 := -7^1 + 2^2 + 4^8 + 3^8 + 7^3$	$72944 := -7^2 - 2^7 + 9^4 + 4^5 + 4^8$
$71578 := -7^2 - 1^0 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^4$	$72439 := -7^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 3^4 + 9^5$	$72946 := -7^3 - 2^5 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 6^5$

$72964 := -7^3 - 2^2 - 9^0 + 6^5 + 4^8$	$73539 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 3^0 + 9^0$	$73667 := 7^4 + 3^3 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 7^5$
$72984 := 7^3 + 2^5 + 9^4 + 8^3 + 4^8$	$73540 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 4^1 - 0^0$	$73686 := -7^1 - 3^9 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 6^6$
$73025 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 0^1 - 2^9 + 5^7$	$73542 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 4^0 + 2^2$	$73697 := -7^4 + 3^5 - 6^0 + 9^5 + 7^5$
$73246 := -7^1 - 3^3 - 2^5 + 4^8 + 6^5$	$73552 := -7^4 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 5^7 + 2^4$	$73752 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 7^3 + 5^7 - 2^7$
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$73264 := -7^1 - 3^2 - 2^5 + 6^5 + 4^8$	$73556 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 5^7 - 6^1$	$73792 := -7^4 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 9^5 + 2^8$
$73285 := -7^1 - 3^6 - 2^3 - 8^4 + 5^7$	$73558 := -7^3 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 8^4$	$73797 := -7^4 - 3^0 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 7^5$
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$73469 := 7^2 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 6^4 + 9^4$	$73604 := 7^2 + 3^5 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 4^8$	$73957 := -7^1 - 3^0 - 9^4 + 5^7 + 7^4$
$73482 := 7^5 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 2^7$	$73625 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 6^3 - 2^7 + 5^7$	$73975 := -7^1 - 3^5 - 9^5 + 7^6 + 5^6$
$73520 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 - 2^4 - 0^0$	$73626 := -7^1 - 3^9 + 6^6 + 2^2 + 6^6$	$74025 := -7^1 - 4^6 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 5^7$
$73522 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 2^0 - 2^4$	$73642 := -7^1 + 3^4 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 2^8$	$74045 := -7^2 - 4^6 + 0^0 + 4^3 + 5^7$
$73528 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 - 2^0 - 8^1$	$73643 := 7^1 + 3^4 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 3^5$	$74085 := -7^1 - 4^6 - 0^0 + 8^2 + 5^7$
$73529 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 2^0 - 9^1$	$73644 := 7^2 + 3^3 + 6^5 + 4^4 + 4^8$	$74168 := 7^3 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 6^5 + 8^3$
$73532 := -7^4 - 3^0 + 5^7 - 3^7 - 2^2$	$73645 := -7^2 - 3^5 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 5^4$	$74233 := -7^2 + 4^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 3^8$
$73533 := -7^4 - 3^0 + 5^7 - 3^1 - 3^7$	$73647 := -7^1 - 3^0 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 7^3$	$74235 := -7^2 - 4^6 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 5^7$
$73534 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 3^0 - 4^1$	$73648 := -7^2 + 3^8 + 6^6 + 4^7 + 8^4$	$74239 := -7^2 + 4^8 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 9^4$
$73535 := -7^1 - 3^6 - 5^5 - 3^6 + 5^7$	$73649 := 7^1 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 4^4 + 9^5$	$74252 := -7^2 - 4^6 + 2^4 + 5^7 + 2^8$
$73537 := -7^4 - 3^0 + 5^7 - 3^7 + 7^0$	$73658 := -7^3 - 3^3 - 6^0 + 5^7 - 8^4$	$74253 := -7^3 + 4^8 - 2^2 + 5^6 - 3^8$
$73538 := -7^4 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 3^2 - 8^1$	$73664 := 7^3 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 6^5 + 4^8$	$74259 := -7^3 - 4^3 - 2^3 + 5^6 + 9^5$
		$74266 := -7^3 + 4^8 + 2^0 + 6^4 + 6^5$
		$74293 := 7^1 + 4^8 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 3^7$
		$74293 := -7^1 + 4^8 + 2^4 + 9^4 + 3^7$

$74295 := -7^3 - 4^1 - 2^5 + 9^5 + 5^6$	$74616 := 7^1 + 4^8 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 6^5$	$74955 := -7^3 - 4^0 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 5^6$
$74296 := -7^4 + 4^7 - 2^5 + 9^5 + 6^4$	$74632 := 7^4 + 4^8 + 6^1 + 3^8 + 2^7$	$74968 := -7^2 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 8^4$
$74323 := 7^1 + 4^8 + 3^7 + 2^5 + 3^8$	$74633 := 7^3 + 4^8 + 6^1 + 3^7 + 3^8$	$74976 := -7^1 + 4^7 - 9^5 + 7^6 - 6^0$
$74334 := 7^2 + 4^0 + 3^7 + 3^8 + 4^8$	$74652 := -7^2 + 4^6 - 6^5 + 5^7 + 2^8$	$74978 := -7^1 + 4^7 - 9^5 + 7^6 + 8^0$
$74345 := 7^4 + 4^6 + 3^7 + 4^8 + 5^3$	$74655 := -7^3 - 4^0 - 6^0 - 5^5 + 5^7$	$74982 := -7^5 + 4^1 + 9^5 + 8^5 - 2^5$
$74346 := 7^1 + 4^5 + 3^1 + 4^8 + 6^5$	$74657 := -7^1 - 4^5 - 6^2 + 5^7 - 7^4$	$74986 := -7^3 - 4^6 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 6^6$
$74349 := 7^2 + 4^2 + 3^7 + 4^8 + 9^4$	$74658 := -7^4 + 4^8 - 6^1 + 5^6 - 8^4$	$74987 := -7^1 - 4^2 + 9^5 + 8^5 - 7^5$
$74359 := -7^3 + 4^0 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$74659 := -7^1 + 4^8 + 6^5 + 5^4 + 9^3$	$74995 := -7^4 - 4^0 + 9^0 - 9^3 + 5^7$
$74363 := 7^5 + 4^6 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 3^8$	$74659 := 7^4 + 4^8 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 9^4$	$75019 := 7^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 1^0 + 9^5$
$74365 := -7^4 - 4^3 + 3^0 - 6^4 + 5^7$	$74665 := -7^4 - 4^5 + 6^0 - 6^2 + 5^7$	$75025 := -7^1 - 5^5 + 0^1 + 2^5 + 5^7$
$74369 := 7^2 + 4^8 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 9^4$	$74685 := -7^4 + 4^4 - 6^4 + 8^0 + 5^7$	$75058 := -7^1 - 5^5 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 8^2$
$74435 := -7^4 - 4^4 - 4^5 - 3^2 + 5^7$	$74695 := -7^1 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 9^5 + 5^6$	$75094 := -7^3 + 5^1 - 0^0 + 9^5 + 4^7$
$74436 := 7^4 + 4^6 + 4^8 + 3^7 + 6^3$	$74696 := 7^1 + 4^8 + 6^4 + 9^2 + 6^5$	$75099 := 7^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 9^2 + 9^5$
$74437 := 7^4 + 4^6 + 4^8 + 3^1 + 7^4$	$74698 := -7^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 9^5 - 8^3$	$75203 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 0^1 - 3^2$
$74445 := -7^4 - 4^4 + 4^0 - 4^5 + 5^7$	$74725 := -7^1 - 4^5 - 7^4 + 2^5 + 5^7$	$75206 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 0^1 - 6^1$
$74452 := -7^4 - 4^4 - 4^5 + 5^7 + 2^3$	$74745 := -7^4 - 4^1 + 7^2 - 4^5 + 5^7$	$75208 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^2 + 0^1 - 8^3$
$74453 := -7^2 - 4^4 - 4^6 + 5^7 + 3^6$	$74750 := -7^4 - 4^5 + 7^2 + 5^7 + 0^0$	$75212 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^0 + 1^0 - 2^9$
$74454 := -7^3 - 4^4 + 4^5 + 5^7 - 4^6$	$74755 := -7^3 - 4^0 - 7^4 - 5^4 + 5^7$	$75214 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 1^0 + 4^0$
$74459 := -7^3 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$74763 := 7^2 + 4^8 + 7^4 + 6^3 + 3^8$	$75220 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 2^3 + 0^1$
$74495 := -7^1 - 4^4 - 4^6 + 9^3 + 5^7$	$74858 := -7^6 - 4^8 - 8^4 - 5^1 + 8^6$	$75221 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 2^3 + 1^0$
$74498 := 7^4 + 4^7 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 8^5$	$74859 := -7^1 + 4^4 - 8^2 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$75222 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 2^3 - 2^9$
$74498 := -7^5 - 4^4 - 4^4 + 9^5 + 8^5$	$74864 := -7^6 - 4^6 + 8^6 + 6^0 - 4^8$	$75223 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 2^1 + 3^2$
$74503 := 7^4 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 3^8$	$74879 := -7^2 + 4^7 - 8^3 + 7^1 + 9^5$	$75224 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 2^3 + 4^1$
$74525 := -7^3 - 4^1 - 5^5 - 2^7 + 5^7$	$74896 := 7^3 + 4^8 + 8^3 + 9^3 + 6^5$	$75225 := -7^4 + 5^1 - 2^9 + 2^3 + 5^7$
$74527 := -7^1 - 4^6 + 5^7 + 2^9 - 7^1$	$74897 := -7^2 - 4^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 - 7^5$	$75226 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 2^3 + 6^1$
$74529 := -7^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 2^5 + 9^5$	$74922 := -7^1 + 4^7 + 9^5 + 2^3 - 2^9$	$75227 := -7^2 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 2^6 - 7^4$
$74585 := -7^3 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 8^1 + 5^7$	$74925 := -7^1 + 4^4 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 5^6$	$75228 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 2^3 + 2^3 - 8^3$
$74587 := -7^2 - 4^5 + 5^7 - 8^2 - 7^4$	$74944 := -7^6 - 4^6 + 9^2 - 4^8 + 4^9$	$75229 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 2^3 + 9^1$
$74592 := -7^2 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 9^5 - 2^5$	$74945 := -7^2 + 4^3 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 5^6$	$75235 := -7^1 - 5^5 - 2^0 + 3^5 + 5^7$
		$75238 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^0 + 3^3 - 8^3$
		$75239 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 2^0 + 3^5 - 9^3$
		$75243 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^3 + 4^4 - 3^6$

$75244 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 4^2$	$75393 := -7^1 + 5^6 - 3^1 + 9^5 + 3^6$	$75532 := -7^1 - 5^5 + 5^7 + 3^3 + 2^9$
$75245 := -7^1 - 5^5 - 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^7$	$75394 := -7^1 - 5^1 - 3^3 + 9^5 + 4^7$	$75533 := -7^4 + 5^2 + 5^7 + 3^3 - 3^5$
$75248 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 4^1 - 8^3$	$75395 := -7^1 - 5^0 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 5^6$	$75534 := -7^3 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 3^7 + 4^3$
$75249 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 9^3$	$75396 := -7^1 + 5^6 + 3^8 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$75536 := -7^4 + 5^0 + 5^7 + 3^3 - 6^3$
$75250 := -7^1 - 5^5 + 2^8 + 5^7 + 0^0$	$75397 := -7^1 + 5^6 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 7^0$	$75537 := -7^2 - 5^5 + 5^7 + 3^5 + 7^3$
$75257 := -7^3 - 5^3 + 2^0 + 5^7 - 7^4$	$75398 := -7^3 + 5^7 - 3^8 + 9^2 + 8^4$	$75538 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 + 3^1 - 8^2$
$75264 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 6^2 + 4^2$	$75399 := -7^1 + 5^6 + 3^1 + 9^3 + 9^5$	$75554 := -7^1 + 5^4 - 5^5 + 5^7 - 4^3$
$75267 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 6^1 + 7^2$	$75404 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 4^3 + 0^1 - 4^4$	$75562 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 6^2 - 2^0$
$75268 := -7^2 + 5^7 - 2^3 + 6^4 - 8^4$	$75409 := -7^2 + 5^2 + 4^7 + 0^1 + 9^5$	$75564 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 6^2 + 4^0$
$75284 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 8^1 + 4^3$	$75425 := -7^3 - 5^5 + 4^4 + 2^9 + 5^7$	$75572 := -7^4 - 5^2 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 2^7$
$75292 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^0 + 9^2 - 2^9$	$75427 := -7^2 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 2^3 - 7^4$	$75573 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 3^3$
$75294 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 9^2 + 4^0$	$75429 := -7^1 + 5^0 + 4^7 + 2^1 + 9^5$	$75575 := -7^2 - 5^3 + 5^2 - 7^4 + 5^7$
$75305 := -7^1 - 5^4 - 3^7 - 0^0 + 5^7$	$75430 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 4^5 + 3^6 + 0^0$	$75582 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 8^0 - 2^4$
$75318 := -7^3 + 5^7 - 3^8 + 1^0 + 8^4$	$75445 := -7^1 - 5^4 - 4^5 - 4^5 + 5^7$	$75584 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 + 8^0 - 4^2$
$75332 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 3^6 + 3^4 + 2^8$	$75448 := -7^4 + 5^2 + 4^7 + 4^8 - 8^4$	$75589 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 8^0 - 9^1$
$75336 := 7^5 + 5^5 + 3^7 + 3^8 + 6^6$	$75449 := 7^1 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 4^7 + 9^5$	$75590 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 9^1 + 0^1$
$75352 := -7^2 - 5^2 - 3^7 + 5^7 - 2^9$	$75449 := -7^2 + 5^0 + 4^3 + 4^7 + 9^5$	$75591 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 9^1 + 1^0$
$75353 := -7^3 + 5^0 - 3^5 + 5^7 - 3^7$	$75465 := -7^1 - 5^5 + 4^4 + 6^3 + 5^7$	$75592 := -7^4 - 5^1 + 5^7 + 9^0 - 2^7$
$75354 := 7^1 + 5^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 4^8$	$75467 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 6^1 - 7^4$	$75593 := -7^3 - 5^0 + 5^7 - 9^0 - 3^7$
$75354 := -7^4 - 5^4 - 3^0 + 5^7 + 4^4$	$75468 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 6^0 - 8^0$	$75594 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 9^0 - 4^1$
$75355 := -7^4 - 5^0 - 3^5 - 5^3 + 5^7$	$75470 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 7^0 + 0^0$	$75595 := -7^4 - 5^1 - 5^3 + 9^0 + 5^7$
$75356 := -7^1 + 5^6 - 3^9 + 5^7 + 6^4$	$75474 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 4^0 + 7^1 - 4^4$	$75596 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 9^1 + 6^1$
$75357 := -7^3 - 5^2 + 3^0 + 5^7 - 7^4$	$75476 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 7^1 + 6^0$	$75597 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 9^0 - 7^0$
$75359 := -7^2 + 5^1 + 3^6 + 5^6 + 9^5$	$75483 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 4^0 + 8^0 - 3^5$	$75598 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 9^1 + 8^1$
$75375 := -7^2 - 5^5 + 3^4 + 7^3 + 5^7$	$75488 := -7^6 + 5^4 - 4^8 + 8^6 - 8^4$	$75599 := -7^2 - 5^5 + 5^7 - 9^2 + 9^3$
$75378 := -7^2 + 5^7 - 3^7 + 7^0 - 8^3$	$75489 := -7^1 - 5^0 + 4^7 + 8^2 + 9^5$	$75602 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 6^1 + 0^1 - 2^7$
$75379 := -7^3 - 5^3 - 3^2 + 7^5 + 9^5$	$75506 := -7^4 - 5^0 + 5^7 - 0^0 - 6^3$	$75605 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 0^1 + 5^7$
$75385 := -7^3 - 5^5 + 3^6 - 8^0 + 5^7$	$75507 := -7^3 + 5^3 + 5^7 + 0^0 - 7^4$	$75622 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 6^1 + 2^5 - 2^7$
$75392 := -7^1 + 5^6 + 3^6 + 9^5 - 2^2$	$75519 := -7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 + 1^0 - 9^2$	$75623 := -7^3 + 5^7 - 6^2 + 2^6 - 3^7$
		$75625 := -7^4 - 5^3 - 6^1 + 2^5 + 5^7$
		$75628 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 6^2 + 2^2 - 8^2$
		$75629 := -7^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 2^1 + 9^5$

$75643 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 6^0 + 4^0 - 3^4$	$75726 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 2^3 + 6^0$	$75768 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^1 + 6^2 + 8^0$
$75645 := -7^3 - 5^5 - 6^2 + 4^5 + 5^7$	$75727 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 7^0$	$75771 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 7^2 - 1^0$
$75654 := -7^4 - 5^1 - 6^0 + 5^7 - 4^3$	$75728 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 8^0$	$75772 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 7^2 - 2^1$
$75658 := -7^4 - 5^0 - 6^0 + 5^7 - 8^2$	$75731 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 3^2 - 1^0$	$75773 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 7^2 - 3^0$
$75662 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 6^0 + 6^0 - 2^6$	$75732 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 3^0 + 2^3$	$75773 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 7^2 + 3^0$
$75675 := -7^2 - 5^0 + 6^0 - 7^4 + 5^7$	$75733 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 3^0 + 3^2$	$75775 := -7^4 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 7^2 + 5^7$
$75677 := -7^2 + 5^7 + 6^0 + 7^0 - 7^4$	$75734 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 3^0 + 4^2$	$75779 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^1 + 7^2 - 9^0$
$75685 := -7^1 - 5^4 - 6^4 - 8^3 + 5^7$	$75735 := -7^4 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 3^2 + 5^7$	$75780 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 - 0^0$
$75688 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 6^2 + 8^0 - 8^0$	$75737 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^1 + 3^3 - 7^4$	$75782 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^0 + 2^6$
$75689 := -7^1 + 5^7 + 6^2 + 8^4 - 9^4$	$75739 := -7^1 + 5^6 + 7^3 + 3^6 + 9^5$	$75783 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^2 + 8^0 + 3^2$
$75690 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 6^2 + 9^0 + 0^0$	$75740 := -7^2 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 4^3 + 0^0$	$75786 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 8^2 - 6^0$
$75692 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 6^0 + 9^0 - 2^5$	$75742 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 2^4$	$75788 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 8^0 + 8^2$
$75696 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 6^0 + 9^1 - 6^2$	$75746 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^1 + 4^2 - 6^0$	$75792 := -7^1 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^5 - 2^5$
$75698 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 6^2 + 9^1 + 8^0$	$75748 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^1 + 4^2 + 8^0$	$75793 := -7^1 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^5 - 3^4$
$75702 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 0^0 - 2^4$	$75750 := -7^4 + 5^2 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 0^1$	$75794 := -7^1 + 5^2 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 4^7$
$75703 := -7^2 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 0^0 + 3^3$	$75751 := -7^4 + 5^2 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 1^0$	$75796 := -7^2 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^5 - 6^1$
$75705 := -7^4 - 5^2 + 7^1 - 0^0 + 5^7$	$75752 := -7^4 - 5^1 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 2^5$	$75797 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 9^2 - 7^4$
$75709 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 0^0 - 9^1$	$75753 := -7^4 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 3^3$	$75798 := -7^2 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 9^5 - 8^1$
$75714 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 1^0 - 4^1$	$75754 := -7^4 + 5^2 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 4^1$	$75799 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 9^0 + 9^2$
$75715 := -7^1 - 5^0 - 7^4 - 1^0 + 5^7$	$75755 := -7^4 - 5^0 + 7^1 + 5^2 + 5^7$	$75804 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 0^1 + 4^2$
$75717 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 1^0 - 7^4$	$75756 := -7^4 - 5^1 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 6^2$	$75820 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 2^5 + 0^1$
$75718 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 1^0 - 8^1$	$75757 := -7^4 + 5^2 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 7^1$	$75821 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 2^5 + 1^0$
$75719 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 1^0 + 9^0$	$75758 := -7^4 + 5^2 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 8^1$	$75822 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 2^1 + 2^5$
$75720 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 2^1 + 0^0$	$75759 := -7^4 - 5^1 + 7^2 + 5^7 - 9^1$	$75823 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^1 + 2^6 + 3^3$
$75722 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 2^0 + 2^2$	$75760 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 6^2 - 0^0$	$75824 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 2^5 + 4^1$
$75723 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 2^0 - 3^0$	$75760 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 6^2 + 0^0$	$75825 := -7^4 + 5^1 + 8^2 + 2^5 + 5^7$
$75724 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 2^3 - 4^0$	$75762 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 6^2 + 2^0$	$75826 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 2^1 + 6^2$
$75725 := -7^4 + 5^0 - 7^0 + 2^0 + 5^7$	$75766 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 7^1 + 6^2 - 6^0$	$75827 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 2^5 + 7^1$
$75725 := -7^4 - 5^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 5^7$	$75767 := -7^1 + 5^7 + 7^2 + 6^0 - 7^4$	$75828 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 8^2$
		$75829 := -7^3 + 5^7 + 8^4 + 2^9 - 9^4$
		$75833 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 3^4$
		$75842 := -7^6 - 5^5 + 8^6 - 4^8 + 2^3$

$75843 := -7^3 + 5^7 - 8^1 + 4^4 - 3^7$	$75934 := -7^1 + 5^6 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 4^5$	$75994 := 7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 4^1$
$75844 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 8^1 + 4^3 + 4^3$	$75934 := 7^5 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$75995 := 7^5 + 5^1 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 5^3$
$75845 := -7^4 + 5^3 - 8^1 + 4^1 + 5^7$	$75935 := -7^1 - 5^1 + 9^1 - 3^7 + 5^7$	$75996 := 7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 6^1$
$75846 := 7^4 + 5^3 + 8^1 + 4^8 + 6^5$	$75937 := 7^2 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 7^5$	$75997 := 7^1 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 7^5$
$75846 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 4^3 - 6^1$	$75939 := 7^5 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 3^4 + 9^5$	$75998 := 7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 8^1$
$75847 := -7^4 + 5^0 - 8^4 + 4^8 + 7^5$	$75942 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 4^0 - 2^9$	$75999 := 7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^1 + 9^5$
$75849 := -7^3 - 5^0 + 8^4 + 4^8 + 9^4$	$75943 := 7^5 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^4$	$76079 := 7^1 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 7^5 + 9^5$
$75850 := -7^4 + 5^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 0^1$	$75946 := 7^5 + 5^2 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^0$	$76149 := 7^5 + 6^2 + 1^0 + 4^4 + 9^5$
$75851 := -7^4 + 5^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 1^0$	$75953 := -7^4 - 5^1 - 9^1 + 5^7 + 3^5$	$76234 := 7^4 + 6^5 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^8$
$75852 := -7^4 + 5^0 - 8^0 + 5^7 + 2^7$	$75954 := -7^4 - 5^2 - 9^0 + 5^7 + 4^4$	$76235 := -7^3 - 6^4 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^7$
$75852 := -7^4 - 5^0 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 2^7$	$75955 := -7^4 + 5^2 + 9^2 + 5^3 + 5^7$	$76236 := -7^5 + 6^6 - 2^9 + 3^5 + 6^6$
$75853 := -7^4 + 5^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 3^1$	$75956 := -7^4 + 5^2 - 9^1 + 5^7 + 6^3$	$76239 := -7^4 + 6^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 9^5$
$75854 := -7^4 + 5^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 4^1$	$75957 := -7^2 + 5^2 + 9^5 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$76245 := -7^3 - 6^0 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^7$
$75855 := -7^4 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 5^3 + 5^7$	$75962 := -7^1 + 5^6 + 9^5 + 6^4 - 2^0$	$76252 := -7^2 - 6^4 - 2^4 + 5^7 - 2^9$
$75856 := -7^4 + 5^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 6^1$	$75963 := 7^5 + 5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 3^4$	$76253 := -7^4 - 6^3 + 2^4 + 5^7 + 3^6$
$75857 := -7^4 + 5^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 7^1$	$75964 := -7^1 + 5^6 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 4^0$	$76255 := -7^2 + 6^4 + 2^3 + 5^7 - 5^5$
$75858 := -7^4 + 5^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 8^1$	$75972 := -7^1 - 5^1 + 9^5 + 7^5 + 2^7$	$76258 := -7^4 + 6^1 + 2^4 + 5^7 + 8^3$
$75859 := -7^4 + 5^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 9^1$	$75973 := -7^1 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 7^5 - 3^0$	$76259 := -7^2 - 6^4 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 9^1$
$75859 := 7^5 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 9^5$	$75974 := 7^2 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 7^5 + 4^3$	$76263 := -7^5 + 6^6 + 2^0 + 6^6 - 3^5$
$75868 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 8^1 + 6^3 - 8^2$	$75975 := -7^1 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 7^5 + 5^3$	$76274 := 7^2 + 6^5 + 2^9 + 7^4 + 4^8$
$75869 := -7^1 + 5^7 + 8^4 + 6^3 - 9^4$	$75978 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 9^2 + 7^3 - 8^1$	$76275 := -7^2 - 6^4 - 2^9 + 7^1 + 5^7$
$75886 := -7^4 - 5^4 - 8^3 + 8^5 + 6^6$	$75982 := -7^4 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 2^8$	$76279 := -7^2 + 6^3 + 2^8 + 7^5 + 9^5$
$75890 := 7^5 + 5^2 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 0^0$	$75983 := 7^5 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 8^0 + 3^0$	$76293 := -7^4 - 6^1 - 2^5 + 9^5 + 3^9$
$75907 := 7^2 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 0^0 + 7^5$	$75987 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 9^2 + 8^0 + 7^3$	$76294 := 7^3 + 6^1 + 2^9 + 9^5 + 4^7$
$75922 := 7^5 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 2^6$	$75990 := 7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 0^1$	$76296 := 7^5 + 6^3 + 2^3 + 9^5 + 6^3$
$75923 := -7^1 + 5^7 - 9^1 + 2^0 - 3^7$	$75991 := 7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 1^0$	$76297 := -7^3 + 6^4 - 2^9 + 9^5 + 7^5$
$75926 := 7^5 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 6^0$	$75992 := 7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 2^1$	$76298 := -7^5 + 6^4 - 2^3 + 9^5 + 8^5$
$75932 := -7^4 + 5^7 - 9^0 + 3^4 + 2^7$	$75993 := -7^3 - 5^5 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^9$	$76299 := 7^4 + 6^5 + 2^9 + 9^4 + 9^5$
$75933 := -7^1 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 3^0 - 3^7$	$75993 := 7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5 + 3^1$	$76325 := -7^3 - 6^3 - 3^6 - 2^9 + 5^7$
		$76326 := -7^5 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 2^6 + 6^6$
		$76329 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 3^9 - 2^0 + 9^5$
		$76329 := 7^5 + 6^3 + 3^0 + 2^8 + 9^5$

$76339 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 3^2 + 3^9 + 9^5$	$76522 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 5^7 - 2^1 - 2^8$	$76583 := -7^2 - 6^5 + 5^7 + 8^4 + 3^7$
$76345 := -7^4 + 6^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^6$	$76523 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 5^7 - 2^8 - 3^0$	$76586 := -7^3 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 8^2 - 6^4$
$76367 := -7^4 - 6^6 - 3^0 + 6^5 + 7^6$	$76524 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 4^4$	$76589 := 7^5 + 6^3 + 5^1 + 8^3 + 9^5$
$76369 := 7^5 + 6^3 + 3^4 + 6^3 + 9^5$	$76525 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 5^0 - 2^8 + 5^7$	$76605 := -7^1 - 6^3 - 6^4 - 0^0 + 5^7$
$76379 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 9^5$	$76526 := -7^1 - 6^4 + 5^7 - 2^9 + 6^3$	$76655 := -7^5 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 5^2 + 5^3$
$76382 := -7^3 + 6^6 - 3^7 + 8^5 - 2^9$	$76527 := -7^3 - 6^4 + 5^7 - 2^3 + 7^2$	$76744 := 7^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 4^8$
$76389 := -7^4 - 6^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 9^5$	$76528 := -7^4 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 2^8 + 8^3$	$76745 := -7^1 - 6^1 - 7^3 - 4^5 + 5^7$
$76394 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 4^3$	$76529 := 7^5 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 2^9 + 9^5$	$76754 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 7^1 + 5^7 + 4^5$
$76405 := -7^5 - 6^4 + 4^7 - 0^0 + 5^7$	$76533 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 5^7 + 3^4 + 3^6$	$76762 := -7^5 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 2^8$
$76443 := 7^4 + 6^5 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 3^6$	$76536 := -7^2 - 6^0 + 5^7 - 3^5 - 6^4$	$76765 := 7^4 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 5^5$
$76445 := 7^1 + 6^5 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 5^5$	$76538 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 5^7 - 3^5 + 8^0$	$76768 := -7^3 - 6^5 + 7^6 + 6^1 - 8^5$
$76449 := -7^1 - 6^0 + 4^5 + 4^7 + 9^5$	$76541 := -7^3 - 6^3 + 5^7 - 4^5 - 1^0$	$76784 := -7^4 - 6^6 + 7^6 + 8^4 + 4^6$
$76452 := 7^1 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 2^3$	$76542 := -7^3 - 6^4 + 5^7 + 4^3 - 2^3$	$76795 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 7^3 + 9^3 + 5^7$
$76452 := -7^2 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 2^6$	$76543 := -7^3 - 6^3 + 5^7 - 4^5 + 3^0$	$76806 := -7^4 - 6^3 + 8^5 - 0^0 + 6^6$
$76453 := 7^1 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 3^2$	$76545 := -7^1 + 6^4 - 5^5 + 4^4 + 5^7$	$76815 := -7^1 - 6^4 - 8^1 + 1^0 + 5^7$
$76453 := -7^4 + 6^0 - 4^0 + 5^7 + 3^6$	$76546 := -7^5 + 6^6 + 5^2 + 4^2 + 6^6$	$76825 := -7^1 - 6^4 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 5^7$
$76453 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 4^0 + 5^7 + 3^6$	$76547 := -7^6 + 6^5 - 5^7 + 4^9 + 7^4$	$76835 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 8^2 - 3^2 + 5^7$
$76454 := -7^3 - 6^4 - 4^2 + 5^7 - 4^2$	$76548 := -7^1 + 6^6 - 5^5 + 4^4 + 8^5$	$76845 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 8^0 + 4^3 + 5^7$
$76454 := 7^4 + 6^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 4^8$	$76549 := -7^3 - 6^4 + 5^7 + 4^3 - 9^0$	$76852 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 2^6$
$76455 := -7^1 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 5^2 + 5^5$	$76562 := -7^2 - 6^3 + 5^7 - 6^4 - 2^1$	$76853 := -7^2 - 6^4 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 3^4$
$76475 := -7^1 - 6^4 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 5^7$	$76563 := -7^2 - 6^3 + 5^7 - 6^4 - 3^0$	$76855 := -7^1 - 6^4 + 8^1 + 5^2 + 5^7$
$76479 := 7^3 + 6^3 + 4^3 + 7^5 + 9^5$	$76564 := -7^5 + 6^6 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 4^3$	$76859 := -7^1 + 6^7 - 8^6 + 5^2 + 9^5$
$76494 := -7^3 + 6^7 - 4^1 + 9^5 - 4^9$	$76565 := -7^2 - 6^3 + 5^0 - 6^4 + 5^7$	$76874 := -7^5 + 6^5 - 8^5 + 7^6 + 4^5$
$76495 := 7^2 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 9^1 + 5^5$	$76566 := -7^5 + 6^2 + 5^2 + 6^6 + 6^6$	$76885 := -7^1 - 6^4 - 8^0 + 8^2 + 5^7$
$76497 := -7^3 + 6^7 - 4^9 + 9^5 - 7^0$	$76568 := -7^5 + 6^6 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 8^2$	$76894 := 7^5 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 4^5$
$76499 := -7^3 + 6^7 - 4^9 + 9^0 + 9^5$	$76569 := -7^2 + 6^5 + 5^6 + 6^6 + 9^4$	$76895 := -7^1 - 6^4 - 8^1 + 9^2 + 5^7$
$76502 := -7^3 - 6^4 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 2^4$	$76578 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 8^3$	$76898 := -7^1 + 6^7 + 8^2 + 9^5 - 8^6$
$76506 := -7^5 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 6^6$	$76579 := -7^4 - 6^0 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 9^5$	$76924 := 7^5 + 6^2 + 9^5 + 2^3 + 4^5$
$76508 := -7^4 + 6^4 + 5^7 + 0^1 - 8^3$	$76582 := -7^3 - 6^4 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 2^5$	$76925 := -7^2 - 6^4 + 9^2 + 2^6 + 5^7$
		$76927 := 7^3 + 6^3 + 9^5 + 2^9 + 7^5$
		$76929 := 7^5 + 6^3 + 9^3 + 2^7 + 9^5$
		$76943 := 7^5 + 6^2 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 3^3$

$76945 := -7^2 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 5^6$	$77464 := 7^1 + 7^2 + 4^6 + 6^5 + 4^8$	$77578 := -7^2 + 7^1 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 8^3$
$76982 := -7^4 + 6^6 - 9^1 + 8^5 - 2^5$	$77473 := -7^5 - 7^5 - 4^0 + 7^6 - 3^8$	$77598 := -7^1 - 7^1 + 5^7 - 9^0 - 8^3$
$76984 := -7^3 + 6^5 - 9^2 + 8^4 + 4^8$	$77485 := -7^2 - 7^3 - 4^4 + 8^1 + 5^7$	$77645 := -7^1 - 7^0 - 6^3 - 4^4 + 5^7$
$76986 := -7^4 - 6^2 - 9^0 + 8^5 + 6^6$	$77490 := -7^3 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 9^5 - 0^0$	$77652 := -7^3 - 7^0 - 6^0 + 5^7 - 2^7$
$77045 := -7^1 - 7^2 + 0^1 - 4^5 + 5^7$	$77492 := -7^3 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 9^5 + 2^0$	$77653 := -7^2 - 7^3 + 6^0 + 5^7 - 3^4$
$77053 := -7^3 - 7^0 + 0^0 + 5^7 - 3^6$	$77496 := 7^3 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 9^5 + 6^4$	$77654 := -7^2 - 7^5 + 6^0 + 5^7 + 4^7$
$77054 := -7^2 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 5^7 - 4^5$	$77502 := -7^3 - 7^3 + 5^7 - 0^0 + 2^6$	$77655 := -7^3 - 7^0 - 6^0 - 5^3 + 5^7$
$77059 := -7^3 + 7^1 - 0^0 + 5^7 - 9^3$	$77504 := -7^3 - 7^3 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 4^3$	$77656 := -7^3 - 7^3 + 6^0 + 5^7 + 6^3$
$77155 := -7^3 - 7^0 - 1^0 - 5^4 + 5^7$	$77516 := -7^2 - 7^3 + 5^7 - 1^0 - 6^3$	$77695 := -7^1 - 7^3 + 6^0 - 9^2 + 5^7$
$77225 := -7^2 - 7^3 + 2^2 - 2^9 + 5^7$	$77519 := -7^3 - 7^3 + 5^7 - 1^0 + 9^2$	$77725 := -7^1 - 7^2 - 7^3 - 2^0 + 5^7$
$77243 := -7^4 + 7^5 - 2^9 + 4^8 - 3^7$	$77520 := -7^1 - 7^3 + 5^7 - 2^8 + 0^0$	$77734 := -7^4 - 7^5 + 7^6 - 3^9 - 4^5$
$77285 := -7^2 - 7^3 + 2^6 - 8^3 + 5^7$	$77524 := -7^3 - 7^0 + 5^7 - 2^0 - 4^4$	$77735 := -7^1 - 7^2 - 7^3 + 3^2 + 5^7$
$77286 := -7^4 + 7^1 + 2^8 + 8^5 + 6^6$	$77526 := -7^3 - 7^0 + 5^7 - 2^8 + 6^0$	$77752 := -7^1 - 7^1 - 7^3 + 5^7 - 2^4$
$77345 := -7^2 - 7^0 - 3^6 - 4^0 + 5^7$	$77531 := -7^1 - 7^3 + 5^7 - 3^5 - 1^0$	$77753 := -7^1 - 7^2 - 7^3 + 5^7 + 3^3$
$77352 := -7^2 + 7^0 - 3^6 + 5^7 + 2^2$	$77533 := -7^1 - 7^3 + 5^7 + 3^0 - 3^5$	$77755 := -7^3 - 7^0 - 7^0 - 5^2 + 5^7$
$77353 := -7^2 + 7^1 - 3^0 + 5^7 - 3^6$	$77534 := -7^3 - 7^0 + 5^7 + 3^2 - 4^4$	$77759 := -7^1 - 7^1 - 7^3 + 5^7 - 9^1$
$77354 := -7^3 - 7^3 - 3^4 + 5^7 - 4^1$	$77537 := -7^3 - 7^0 + 5^7 - 3^5 - 7^0$	$77775 := -7^1 - 7^0 + 7^0 - 7^3 + 5^7$
$77355 := -7^2 + 7^1 - 3^6 + 5^0 + 5^7$	$77539 := -7^3 - 7^0 + 5^7 - 3^5 + 9^0$	$77785 := -7^3 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 5^7$
$77357 := -7^3 - 7^0 - 3^4 + 5^7 - 7^3$	$77552 := -7^1 - 7^2 - 5^1 + 5^7 - 2^9$	$77825 := -7^3 + 7^2 - 8^1 + 2^1 + 5^7$
$77358 := -7^3 + 7^1 + 3^4 + 5^7 - 8^3$	$77556 := -7^1 - 7^3 + 5^6 + 5^6 + 6^6$	$77835 := -7^3 + 7^2 + 8^0 + 3^1 + 5^7$
$77359 := -7^3 - 7^3 + 3^0 + 5^7 - 9^2$	$77557 := -7^1 - 7^3 + 5^3 + 5^7 - 7^3$	$77845 := -7^3 + 7^1 - 8^1 + 4^3 + 5^7$
$77375 := -7^1 - 7^1 - 3^6 - 7^1 + 5^7$	$77558 := -7^1 + 7^0 - 5^4 + 5^7 + 8^2$	$77849 := 7^1 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 4^7 + 9^5$
$77396 := 7^5 + 7^0 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 6^4$	$77560 := -7^1 - 7^3 + 5^7 - 6^3 + 0^0$	$77849 := -7^2 + 7^4 + 8^2 + 4^7 + 9^5$
$77425 := -7^3 - 7^3 - 4^2 + 2^1 + 5^7$	$77562 := -7^2 - 7^0 + 5^7 - 6^0 - 2^9$	$77852 := -7^3 + 7^1 - 8^0 + 5^7 + 2^6$
$77435 := -7^3 - 7^3 - 4^0 - 3^1 + 5^7$	$77564 := -7^3 - 7^0 + 5^7 - 6^3 - 4^0$	$77854 := -7^1 - 7^1 - 8^0 + 5^7 - 4^4$
$77445 := -7^5 - 7^0 - 4^4 + 4^7 + 5^7$	$77565 := -7^3 - 7^3 + 5^3 + 6^0 + 5^7$	$77855 := -7^3 + 7^2 - 8^0 + 5^2 + 5^7$
$77454 := -7^3 - 7^3 - 4^0 + 5^7 + 4^2$	$77566 := -7^3 - 7^0 + 5^7 + 6^0 - 6^3$	$77865 := -7^1 - 7^2 - 8^5 - 6^7 + 5^8$
$77456 := -7^3 - 7^3 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 6^0$	$77572 := -7^2 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 2^9$	$77932 := -7^3 + 7^6 - 9^5 + 3^9 - 2^3$
$77462 := -7^4 + 7^5 + 4^7 + 6^6 + 2^4$	$77574 := -7^3 - 7^0 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 4^4$	$77935 := -7^3 + 7^6 - 9^5 + 3^9 - 5^1$
		$77939 := -7^3 + 7^6 - 9^0 + 3^9 - 9^5$
		$77945 := -7^2 - 7^2 - 9^2 - 4^0 + 5^7$
		$77952 := -7^3 - 7^3 + 9^0 + 5^7 + 2^9$

$77954 := -7^2 - 7^2 - 9^1 + 5^7 - 4^3$	$78235 := -7^1 - 8^1 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^7$	$78353 := -7^1 + 8^0 - 3^2 + 5^7 + 3^5$
$77955 := -7^3 + 7^2 - 9^0 + 5^3 + 5^7$	$78245 := -7^1 - 8^0 + 2^6 + 4^3 + 5^7$	$78354 := -7^1 - 8^1 + 3^5 + 5^7 + 4^0$
$77958 := -7^1 + 7^3 + 9^1 + 5^7 - 8^3$	$78252 := -7^1 + 8^1 - 2^1 + 5^7 + 2^7$	$78355 := -7^1 - 8^0 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 5^7$
$77978 := -7^3 + 7^0 - 9^4 + 7^6 - 8^5$	$78253 := 7^1 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 5^7 + 3^4$	$78356 := -7^1 + 8^0 + 3^5 + 5^7 - 6^1$
$77993 := -7^2 + 7^5 - 9^0 + 9^5 + 3^7$	$78253 := -7^1 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 5^7 - 3^0$	$78359 := -7^1 - 8^0 + 3^5 + 5^7 - 9^0$
$77995 := -7^2 - 7^0 + 9^0 - 9^2 + 5^7$	$78254 := -7^1 + 8^1 + 2^6 + 5^7 + 4^3$	$78365 := 7^1 + 8^1 + 3^2 + 6^3 + 5^7$
$78035 := -7^1 - 8^0 - 0^0 - 3^4 + 5^7$	$78254 := 7^2 + 8^1 + 2^3 + 5^7 + 4^3$	$78365 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 3^4 + 6^3 + 5^7$
$78045 := -7^1 - 8^1 - 0^0 - 4^3 + 5^7$	$78255 := -7^1 + 8^1 + 2^2 + 5^3 + 5^7$	$78385 := -7^3 + 8^2 + 3^3 + 8^3 + 5^7$
$78046 := -7^4 + 8^5 - 0^0 + 4^5 + 6^6$	$78255 := 7^2 + 8^2 + 2^4 + 5^0 + 5^7$	$78387 := -7^4 - 8^4 + 3^1 - 8^5 + 7^6$
$78052 := -7^1 - 8^0 - 0^0 + 5^7 - 2^6$	$78256 := -7^3 + 8^3 - 2^1 + 5^7 - 6^2$	$78389 := -7^3 - 8^0 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 9^5$
$78053 := -7^1 - 8^2 + 0^1 + 5^7 - 3^0$	$78259 := -7^1 + 8^2 - 2^2 + 5^7 + 9^2$	$78390 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 0^1$
$78054 := -7^1 - 8^0 + 0^0 + 5^7 - 4^3$	$78273 := -7^2 - 8^5 + 2^1 + 7^6 - 3^8$	$78391 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 1^0$
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$78085 := -7^2 + 8^0 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 5^7$	$78293 := -7^3 - 8^2 - 2^5 + 9^5 + 3^9$	$78396 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 6^1$
$78115 := -7^1 - 8^0 - 1^0 - 1^0 + 5^7$	$78295 := -7^1 + 8^2 + 2^5 + 9^2 + 5^7$	$78397 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 7^1$
$78125 := -7^1 - 8^1 - 1^0 + 2^4 + 5^7$	$78295 := 7^2 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 9^2 + 5^7$	$78398 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 8^1$
$78135 := 7^1 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 5^7$	$78297 := -7^1 - 8^5 - 2^4 - 9^4 + 7^6$	$78399 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 3^9 + 9^1 + 9^5$
$78145 := 7^1 + 8^1 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 5^7$	$78297 := 7^4 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 9^5 + 7^5$	$78438 := -7^6 - 8^3 - 4^8 - 3^2 + 8^6$
$78145 := -7^2 + 8^2 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 5^7$	$78325 := 7^1 + 8^2 + 3^0 + 2^7 + 5^7$	$78446 := -7^6 - 8^3 - 4^8 + 4^9 - 6^0$
$78152 := -7^1 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 5^7 + 2^5$	$78325 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 3^0 + 2^8 + 5^7$	$78448 := -7^6 + 8^0 - 4^8 + 4^9 - 8^3$
$78156 := -7^1 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 5^7 + 6^2$	$78329 := -7^3 - 8^2 + 3^9 + 2^2 + 9^5$	$78452 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 4^4 + 5^7 + 2^7$
$78159 := -7^2 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 5^7 + 9^2$	$78335 := -7^1 + 8^0 - 3^3 + 3^5 + 5^7$	$78453 := 7^1 + 8^2 + 4^4 + 5^7 + 3^0$
$78205 := 7^1 + 8^1 + 2^6 + 0^0 + 5^7$	$78342 := -7^3 + 8^5 - 3^9 + 4^8 + 2^6$	$78453 := -7^4 - 8^2 + 4^8 + 5^6 - 3^5$
$78205 := -7^2 + 8^0 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 5^7$	$78345 := -7^2 - 8^3 - 3^5 + 4^5 + 5^7$	$78454 := -7^1 + 8^2 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 4^4$
$78215 := -7^1 + 8^2 + 2^5 + 1^0 + 5^7$	$78349 := 7^4 + 8^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 9^5$	$78454 := 7^2 + 8^1 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 4^4$
$78215 := 7^2 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 1^0 + 5^7$	$78352 := -7^1 - 8^0 + 3^5 + 5^7 - 2^3$	$78455 := -7^3 + 8^2 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 5^7$
		$78456 := -7^3 - 8^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 6^6$
		$78457 := -7^1 - 8^1 + 4^1 + 5^7 + 7^3$
		$78475 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 4^3 + 7^3 + 5^7$

$78485 := -7^1 + 8^0 - 4^8 + 8^7 - 5^9$	$78541 := 7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 1^0$	$78587 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 8^3 + 7^1$
$78485 := 7^3 + 8^1 + 4^0 + 8^1 + 5^7$	$78542 := 7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 2^1$	$78588 := -7^2 - 8^0 + 5^7 + 8^0 + 8^3$
$78495 := 7^2 + 8^2 + 4^4 + 9^0 + 5^7$	$78542 := -7^3 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^4 + 2^9$	$78589 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 8^3 + 9^1$
$78495 := -7^5 + 8^2 + 4^7 + 9^3 + 5^7$	$78543 := 7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 3^1$	$78590 := -7^2 + 8^3 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 0^0$
$78502 := -7^1 + 8^3 + 5^7 + 0^1 - 2^7$	$78543 := -7^4 + 8^3 + 5^6 + 4^8 - 3^6$	$78592 := -7^1 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 9^3 - 2^8$
$78502 := 7^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 2^5$	$78544 := 7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^1 + 4^3$	$78593 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 9^2 + 3^6$
$78503 := 7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 3^3$	$78545 := 7^3 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 4^3 + 5^7$	$78595 := 7^3 + 8^0 + 5^3 + 9^0 + 5^7$
$78503 := -7^3 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 3^6$	$78545 := -7^3 + 8^3 - 5^1 + 4^4 + 5^7$	$78596 := -7^2 + 8^3 + 5^7 + 9^1 - 6^0$
$78505 := -7^1 + 8^3 - 5^3 + 0^1 + 5^7$	$78546 := 7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 6^1$	$78598 := -7^2 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 9^1 + 8^3$
$78506 := 7^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 6^2$	$78547 := 7^1 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 7^3$	$78625 := -7^1 + 8^0 - 6^1 + 2^9 + 5^7$
$78509 := -7^3 - 8^0 + 5^7 - 0^0 + 9^3$	$78547 := -7^2 + 8^2 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 7^3$	$78635 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 6^4 - 3^6 + 5^7$
$78513 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 1^0 + 3^6$	$78548 := 7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 8^1$	$78638 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 6^6 - 3^6 + 8^5$
$78522 := -7^2 - 8^2 + 5^7 - 2^1 + 2^9$	$78549 := -7^1 - 8^3 + 5^7 + 4^5 - 9^2$	$78639 := -7^2 - 8^1 - 6^2 + 3^9 + 9^5$
$78523 := -7^2 - 8^2 + 5^7 + 2^9 - 3^0$	$78549 := 7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 9^1$	$78645 := -7^1 + 8^3 - 6^0 + 4^2 + 5^7$
$78524 := 7^1 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 2^7 + 4^4$	$78558 := 7^3 + 8^0 + 5^2 + 5^7 + 8^2$	$78647 := -7^4 + 8^0 - 6^4 + 4^8 + 7^5$
$78524 := -7^2 + 8^2 + 5^7 + 2^7 + 4^4$	$78562 := -7^2 + 8^3 + 5^7 + 6^1 - 2^5$	$78650 := 7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 0^1$
$78525 := -7^2 - 8^2 + 5^0 + 2^9 + 5^7$	$78563 := -7^1 + 8^5 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 3^6$	$78651 := 7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 1^0$
$78526 := -7^1 + 8^2 + 5^7 + 2^7 + 6^3$	$78563 := 7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 6^1 + 3^4$	$78652 := 7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 2^1$
$78526 := 7^2 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 2^7 + 6^3$	$78565 := -7^3 - 8^3 - 5^0 + 6^4 + 5^7$	$78652 := -7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 2^4$
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$78527 := 7^2 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 7^3$	$78568 := -7^3 - 8^3 - 5^0 + 6^6 + 8^5$	$78653 := -7^2 + 8^2 - 6^3 + 5^7 + 3^6$
$78528 := -7^2 - 8^2 + 5^7 + 2^2 + 8^3$	$78569 := 7^3 + 8^2 + 5^7 + 6^2 + 9^0$	$78654 := -7^1 + 8^2 + 6^3 + 5^7 + 4^4$
$78534 := 7^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 3^0 + 4^3$	$78580 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 8^3 + 0^1$	$78654 := 7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 4^1$
$78535 := -7^3 - 8^0 + 5^2 + 3^6 + 5^7$	$78581 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 8^3 + 1^0$	$78655 := 7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^1 + 5^7$
$78536 := -7^2 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 3^5 + 6^3$	$78582 := -7^1 - 8^2 + 5^7 + 8^3 + 2^4$	$78656 := 7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 6^1$
$78536 := 7^3 + 8^2 + 5^7 + 3^1 + 6^0$	$78583 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 8^3 + 3^1$	$78657 := 7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 7^1$
$78538 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 3^5 + 8^3$	$78584 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 8^3 + 4^1$	$78658 := 7^1 + 8^1 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 8^3$
$78539 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 3^3 + 9^3$	$78585 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 5^1 + 8^3 + 5^7$	$78658 := -7^1 - 8^1 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 8^3$
$78540 := 7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 0^1$	$78586 := -7^1 - 8^1 + 5^7 + 8^3 - 6^2$	$78659 := 7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 9^1$
		$78665 := -7^1 + 8^3 - 6^0 + 6^2 + 5^7$
		$78689 := -7^1 + 8^0 + 6^6 + 8^5 - 9^3$
		$78695 := -7^1 + 8^2 - 6^3 + 9^3 + 5^7$

$78725 := -7^1 + 8^1 + 7^3 + 2^8 + 5^7$	$78986 := -7^1 - 8^3 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 6^6$	$79394 := 7^1 + 9^3 + 3^8 + 9^4 + 4^8$
$78725 := 7^1 + 8^3 + 7^2 + 2^5 + 5^7$	$79045 := 7^5 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 4^3 + 5^5$	$79442 := -7^3 + 9^5 + 4^6 + 4^7 + 2^8$
$78745 := -7^1 - 8^1 - 7^4 + 4^8 + 5^6$	$79083 := 7^3 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 3^9$	$79448 := -7^1 - 9^4 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 8^4$
$78754 := -7^1 + 8^0 - 7^4 + 5^6 + 4^8$	$79203 := 7^3 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 3^9$	$79454 := 7^3 + 9^3 + 4^0 + 5^7 + 4^4$
$78783 := -7^2 - 8^5 + 7^6 + 8^3 - 3^8$	$79205 := 7^3 + 9^3 + 2^3 + 0^1 + 5^7$	$79480 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 0^1$
$78836 := -7^2 - 8^3 + 8^5 - 3^3 + 6^6$	$79236 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 2^9 + 3^9 - 6^0$	$79481 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 1^0$
$78845 := -7^2 + 8^0 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 5^7$	$79238 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 8^3$	$79482 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 2^1$
$78852 := -7^2 + 8^1 + 8^3 + 5^7 + 2^8$	$79245 := 7^1 + 9^2 + 2^3 + 4^5 + 5^7$	$79483 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 3^1$
$78852 := 7^3 + 8^2 + 8^2 + 5^7 + 2^8$	$79245 := -7^2 + 9^2 + 2^6 + 4^5 + 5^7$	$79484 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^1 + 8^4 + 4^7$
$78855 := -7^3 - 8^2 + 8^3 + 5^4 + 5^7$	$79265 := 7^3 + 9^3 + 2^5 + 6^2 + 5^7$	$79485 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 5^1$
$78857 := -7^2 - 8^5 - 8^6 + 5^8 - 7^5$	$79283 := 7^1 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 8^3 + 3^9$	$79486 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 - 6^2$
$78862 := -7^2 - 8^0 + 8^5 + 6^6 - 2^9$	$79285 := -7^2 + 9^3 - 2^5 + 8^3 + 5^7$	$79486 := 7^2 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 6^6$
$78864 := -7^2 - 8^3 + 8^5 + 6^6 + 4^0$	$79286 := -7^2 - 9^2 - 2^3 + 8^5 + 6^6$	$79487 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 7^1$
$78866 := -7^3 + 8^0 + 8^5 + 6^6 - 6^3$	$79332 := 7^1 + 9^5 + 3^4 + 3^9 + 2^9$	$79488 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 8^1 + 8^4$
$78875 := -7^3 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 7^5 - 5^5$	$79334 := 7^3 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 3^9 + 4^4$	$79489 := -7^2 + 9^1 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 9^5$
$78893 := -7^3 - 8^1 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 3^9$	$79335 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 3^9 + 5^4$	$79532 := -7^2 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 3^6 - 2^1$
$78894 := -7^6 - 8^2 + 8^6 - 9^0 - 4^8$	$79350 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 0^1$	$79533 := -7^2 - 9^0 + 5^7 + 3^6 + 3^6$
$78896 := -7^1 - 8^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 + 6^6$	$79351 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 1^0$	$79534 := 7^3 + 9^2 + 5^7 + 3^6 + 4^4$
$78905 := 7^2 + 8^0 + 9^3 + 0^0 + 5^7$	$79352 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 2^1$	$79534 := -7^3 - 9^0 + 5^7 + 3^6 + 4^5$
$78925 := -7^2 - 8^1 + 9^3 + 2^7 + 5^7$	$79352 := 7^3 + 9^3 + 3^3 + 5^7 + 2^7$	$79535 := -7^2 + 9^3 + 5^0 + 3^6 + 5^7$
$78943 := -7^3 + 8^4 + 9^5 + 4^7 - 3^5$	$79353 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 5^4 + 3^9$	$79536 := 7^1 + 9^2 + 5^7 + 3^3 + 6^4$
$78949 := -7^6 + 8^2 - 9^4 + 4^9 - 9^5$	$79354 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 4^1$	$79538 := -7^3 + 9^2 + 5^7 + 3^7 - 8^3$
$78962 := -7^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 + 6^6 - 2^7$	$79355 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 5^4$	$79553 := -7^1 + 9^2 + 5^4 + 5^7 + 3^6$
$78963 := 7^1 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 3^9$	$79356 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 6^1$	$79555 := -7^2 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 5^4 + 5^7$
$78963 := -7^2 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 3^9$	$79357 := -7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 7^1$	$79556 := 7^2 + 9^2 + 5^1 + 5^7 + 6^4$
$78964 := -7^6 + 8^6 - 9^0 + 6^1 - 4^8$	$79358 := -7^1 - 9^0 + 3^6 + 5^7 + 8^3$	$79557 := -7^2 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 5^5 + 7^5$
$78965 := -7^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 + 6^6 - 5^3$	$79359 := -7^1 + 9^1 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 9^5$	$79559 := -7^2 + 9^3 + 5^2 + 5^7 + 9^3$
$78966 := -7^6 + 8^6 - 9^5 + 6^4 - 6^5$	$79359 := 7^3 + 9^2 + 3^4 + 5^7 + 9^3$	$79572 := 7^3 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 2^5$
$78975 := -7^1 + 8^0 + 9^5 + 7^5 + 5^5$	$79365 := 7^1 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 6^0 + 5^4$	$79574 := 7^3 + 9^2 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 4^5$
		$79576 := 7^3 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 6^2$
		$79590 := 7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 0^1$
		$79591 := 7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 1^0$

$79592 := 7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 2^1$	$79864 := 7^3 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 6^6 + 4^2$	$80589 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 5^7 - 8^0 + 9^4$
$79592 := -7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 2^4$	$79865 := -7^4 + 9^1 + 8^4 + 6^2 + 5^7$	$80590 := -8^4 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 9^4 - 0^0$
$79593 := 7^1 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 3^9$	$79885 := 7^1 + 9^3 + 8^3 + 8^3 + 5^7$	$80591 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 1^0$
$79594 := 7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 4^1$	$79885 := -7^4 + 9^0 + 8^2 + 8^4 + 5^7$	$80592 := -8^4 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 2^0$
$79594 := -7^4 + 9^4 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 4^7$	$79886 := -7^2 - 9^0 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 6^6$	$80593 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 3^1$
$79595 := 7^1 + 9^3 + 5^1 + 9^3 + 5^7$	$79932 := 7^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 2^7$	$80594 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 4^1$
$79596 := 7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 6^1$	$79935 := 7^3 + 9^1 + 9^3 + 3^6 + 5^7$	$80595 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 5^7$
$79596 := -7^3 + 9^4 + 5^6 + 9^5 - 6^4$	$79953 := 7^3 + 9^3 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 3^3$	$80596 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 6^1$
$79597 := 7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 7^1$	$79954 := 7^5 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 4^6$	$80597 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 7^1$
$79598 := 7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 8^1$	$79958 := 7^5 + 9^0 + 9^5 + 5^1 + 8^4$	$80598 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 8^1$
$79598 := -7^2 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 8^2$	$79975 := 7^2 + 9^3 + 9^3 + 7^3 + 5^7$	$80599 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 9^1 + 9^4$
$79599 := 7^1 + 9^1 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 9^3$	$79996 := 7^2 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 9^5 + 6^5$	$80654 := -8^3 - 0^0 + 6^1 + 5^6 + 4^8$
$79623 := 7^3 + 9^5 + 6^2 + 2^9 + 3^9$	$80253 := -8^2 + 0^0 + 2^2 + 5^7 + 3^7$	$80664 := 8^5 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 6^6 + 4^5$
$79642 := 7^4 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 2^9$	$80274 := -8^5 + 0^0 - 2^9 + 7^6 - 4^6$	$80754 := -8^2 + 0^1 - 7^3 + 5^6 + 4^8$
$79682 := -7^1 + 9^1 + 6^6 + 8^5 + 2^8$	$80305 := -8^1 + 0^0 + 3^7 + 0^1 + 5^7$	$80778 := -8^4 + 0^1 - 7^1 + 7^6 - 8^5$
$79682 := 7^2 + 9^2 + 6^6 + 8^5 + 2^7$	$80325 := 8^1 + 0^0 + 3^7 + 2^2 + 5^7$	$80782 := -8^4 - 0^0 + 7^6 - 8^5 - 2^1$
$79683 := 7^1 + 9^1 + 6^6 + 8^5 + 3^5$	$80352 := 8^1 + 0^1 + 3^7 + 5^7 + 2^5$	$80783 := -8^4 - 0^0 + 7^6 - 8^5 - 3^0$
$79685 := -7^3 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 8^5 - 5^3$	$80356 := 8^1 + 0^1 + 3^7 + 5^7 + 6^2$	$80784 := -8^4 - 0^0 + 7^6 + 8^5 - 4^8$
$79687 := -7^2 + 9^5 - 6^3 + 8^4 + 7^5$	$80385 := 8^1 + 0^0 + 3^7 + 8^2 + 5^7$	$80785 := -8^4 - 0^0 + 7^6 - 8^5 + 5^0$
$79738 := -7^4 + 9^5 + 7^5 + 3^7 + 8^4$	$80394 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 3^9 - 9^3 + 4^8$	$80786 := -8^4 + 0^1 + 7^6 - 8^5 + 6^0$
$79752 := -7^2 - 9^3 + 7^4 + 5^7 + 2^2$	$80396 := 8^5 + 0^1 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^6$	$80794 := -8^5 + 0^1 + 7^6 + 9^1 - 4^6$
$79756 := -7^1 - 9^0 + 7^3 + 5^7 + 6^4$	$80457 := -8^2 - 0^0 - 4^1 + 5^7 + 7^4$	$81345 := 8^1 + 1^0 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^7$
$79756 := 7^3 + 9^3 + 7^3 + 5^7 + 6^3$	$80464 := 8^5 + 0^1 + 4^2 + 6^6 + 4^5$	$81434 := -8^3 - 1^0 + 4^7 + 3^3 + 4^8$
$79758 := 7^2 + 9^3 + 7^3 + 5^7 + 8^3$	$80517 := -8^1 + 0^1 + 5^7 - 1^0 + 7^4$	$81452 := -8^3 - 1^0 + 4^6 + 5^7 - 2^8$
$79759 := 7^2 + 9^3 + 7^5 + 5^5 + 9^5$	$80527 := -8^1 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 2^3 + 7^4$	$81454 := -8^3 + 1^0 - 4^4 + 5^7 + 4^6$
$79825 := -7^4 + 9^0 + 8^4 + 2^2 + 5^7$	$80536 := 8^1 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 3^7 + 6^3$	$81563 := -8^4 + 1^0 + 5^7 + 6^5 - 3^5$
$79826 := -7^3 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 2^4 + 6^6$	$80537 := 8^1 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 3^1 + 7^4$	$81582 := -8^3 + 1^0 + 5^7 + 8^4 - 2^7$
$79843 := 7^3 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 3^9$	$80562 := 8^5 + 0^0 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 2^9$	$81585 := -8^3 + 1^0 - 5^3 + 8^4 + 5^7$
$79845 := -7^4 + 9^1 + 8^4 + 4^2 + 5^7$	$80584 := -8^2 - 0^0 + 5^6 - 8^3 + 4^8$	$81613 := 8^5 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 3^7$
		$81693 := 8^5 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 3^7$
		$81749 := -8^3 - 1^0 + 7^5 + 4^8 - 9^2$
		$81754 := -8^5 - 1^0 + 7^6 - 5^5 - 4^0$

$81756 := -8^5 - 1^0 + 7^6 - 5^5 + 6^0$	$82356 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 6^1$	$82468 := 8^5 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 8^5$
$82048 := 8^5 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 8^5$	$82357 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 7^1$	$82472 := 8^2 + 2^0 + 4^8 + 7^5 + 2^6$
$82085 := -8^1 - 2^7 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 5^7$	$82357 := -8^5 - 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^5 + 7^6$	$82477 := -8^5 + 2^0 - 4^1 + 7^6 - 7^4$
$82154 := -8^2 - 2^1 - 1^0 + 5^7 + 4^6$	$82358 := -8^1 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 5^7 + 8^4$	$82485 := -8^1 + 2^4 + 4^4 + 8^4 + 5^7$
$82158 := -8^2 + 2^1 - 1^0 + 5^7 + 8^4$	$82358 := 8^1 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 8^4$	$82487 := 8^1 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 8^1 + 7^5$
$82225 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 5^7$	$82359 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 9^1$	$82527 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 5^7 + 2^8 + 7^2$
$82235 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 3^2 + 5^7$	$82374 := -8^5 - 2^6 - 3^7 + 7^6 - 4^4$	$82532 := 8^4 + 2^2 + 5^7 + 3^5 + 2^6$
$82244 := 8^2 + 2^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 4^8$	$82378 := 8^5 + 2^3 + 3^3 + 7^5 + 8^5$	$82536 := -8^4 + 2^1 + 5^7 + 3^6 + 6^5$
$82245 := 8^1 + 2^3 + 2^3 + 4^6 + 5^7$	$82396 := -8^4 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 6^5$	$82537 := -8^5 - 2^5 - 5^3 - 3^7 + 7^6$
$82245 := -8^1 + 2^4 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^7$	$82407 := -8^2 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 0^1 + 7^5$	$82542 := 8^2 + 2^0 + 5^7 + 4^6 + 2^8$
$82247 := -8^2 - 2^4 - 2^4 + 4^8 + 7^5$	$82424 := -8^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 2^8 + 4^8$	$82553 := 8^4 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 5^7 + 3^5$
$82253 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 5^7 + 3^3$	$82427 := 8^2 + 2^2 + 4^8 + 2^4 + 7^5$	$82554 := 8^3 + 2^8 + 5^4 + 5^6 + 4^8$
$82254 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^4 + 5^7 + 4^2$	$82434 := 8^3 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 3^0 + 4^8$	$82556 := 8^1 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 5^7 + 6^4$
$82255 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^3 + 5^2 + 5^7$	$82437 := -8^5 - 2^0 - 4^4 - 3^7 + 7^6$	$82559 := 8^4 + 2^8 + 5^0 + 5^7 + 9^2$
$82256 := 8^4 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 5^7 + 6^0$	$82440 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 0^1$	$82566 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 5^7 + 6^0 + 6^3$
$82258 := 8^4 + 2^2 + 2^5 + 5^7 + 8^0$	$82441 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 1^0$	$82567 := 8^4 + 2^1 + 5^7 + 6^0 + 7^3$
$82265 := 8^4 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 6^2 + 5^7$	$82442 := 8^1 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 2^9$	$82572 := 8^4 + 2^2 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 2^2$
$82274 := -8^2 - 2^0 - 2^2 + 7^5 + 4^8$	$82443 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 3^1$	$82573 := 8^4 + 2^3 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 3^0$
$82275 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 7^2 + 5^7$	$82444 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 4^7 + 4^8$	$82573 := -8^5 + 2^2 - 5^3 + 7^6 - 3^7$
$82285 := -8^1 + 2^3 + 2^6 + 8^4 + 5^7$	$82445 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 5^1$	$82574 := 8^1 + 2^1 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 4^6$
$82295 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 2^6 + 9^1 + 5^7$	$82445 := -8^2 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 4^6 + 5^7$	$82593 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 3^5$
$82305 := 8^4 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 0^0 + 5^7$	$82446 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 6^1$	$82597 := 8^4 + 2^5 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 7^3$
$82335 := 8^4 + 2^5 + 3^0 + 3^4 + 5^7$	$82447 := 8^1 + 2^5 + 4^3 + 4^8 + 7^5$	$82643 := -8^2 - 2^4 + 6^6 + 4^7 + 3^9$
$82350 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 0^1$	$82447 := -8^1 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 4^8 + 7^5$	$82643 := 8^5 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 4^5 + 3^7$
$82351 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 1^0$	$82448 := 8^1 + 2^3 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 8^3$	$82645 := -8^4 + 2^3 - 6^5 + 4^7 + 5^7$
$82352 := 8^4 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 2^7$	$82449 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 9^1$	$82645 := 8^5 + 2^5 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 5^5$
$82353 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 3^1$	$82449 := -8^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 9^2$	$82648 := 8^5 + 2^9 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 8^5$
$82354 := 8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 4^1$	$82457 := -8^3 + 2^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 + 7^5$	$82663 := -8^4 + 2^3 + 6^6 + 6^6 - 3^8$
$82355 := 8^3 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 5^5 + 5^7$	$82465 := -8^1 + 2^4 + 4^8 + 6^4 + 5^6$	$82685 := 8^1 + 2^7 + 6^6 + 8^5 + 5^5$

$82735 := 8^4 + 2^9 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 5^7$	$83459 := -8^2 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^7 + 9^4$	$83697 := 8^2 + 3^0 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 7^5$
$82735 := -8^4 - 2^8 + 7^4 + 3^8 + 5^7$	$83475 := -8^5 + 3^5 - 4^5 + 7^6 - 5^4$	$83742 := -8^5 - 3^5 + 7^6 - 4^5 + 2^7$
$82737 := -8^5 + 2^8 - 7^4 + 3^0 + 7^6$	$83477 := -8^5 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 7^4 + 7^6$	$83745 := 8^1 + 3^7 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 5^7$
$82753 := 8^1 + 2^5 + 7^4 + 5^7 + 3^7$	$83493 := -8^2 + 3^6 + 4^6 + 9^5 + 3^9$	$83747 := -8^5 + 3^5 - 7^4 + 4^5 + 7^6$
$82773 := -8^5 + 2^7 - 7^2 + 7^6 - 3^7$	$83523 := 8^3 + 3^7 + 5^7 + 2^9 + 3^7$	$83749 := -8^5 - 3^3 + 7^6 - 4^5 - 9^2$
$82774 := 8^5 + 2^3 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$83526 := 8^4 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 2^3 + 6^4$	$83764 := 8^5 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 6^6 + 4^6$
$82776 := -8^5 + 2^9 - 7^4 + 7^6 - 6^3$	$83543 := 8^3 + 3^4 + 5^7 + 4^6 + 3^6$	$83767 := -8^5 - 3^2 - 7^4 + 6^4 + 7^6$
$82855 := 8^1 + 2^0 + 8^4 + 5^4 + 5^7$	$83546 := 8^5 + 3^0 + 5^2 + 4^6 + 6^6$	$83784 := -8^2 - 3^2 + 7^6 - 8^5 - 4^5$
$82887 := 8^3 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 7^5$	$83546 := -8^6 + 3^5 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 6^7$	$83847 := -8^5 - 3^2 - 8^0 - 4^5 + 7^6$
$82893 := 8^2 + 2^0 + 8^4 + 9^5 + 3^9$	$83550 := -8^3 + 3^8 - 5^4 + 5^7 + 0^0$	$83854 := -8^2 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 5^7 - 4^4$
$82937 := 8^1 + 2^9 + 9^5 + 3^8 + 7^5$	$83567 := 8^4 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 6^4 + 7^2$	$83856 := -8^2 + 3^9 + 8^5 + 5^7 - 6^6$
$82952 := 8^4 + 2^0 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 2^0$	$83569 := -8^2 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 6^5 - 9^2$	$83874 := -8^2 + 3^4 - 8^5 + 7^6 - 4^5$
$82953 := 8^4 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 5^7 + 3^6$	$83586 := -8^2 - 3^7 + 5^7 - 8^2 + 6^5$	$83896 := -8^2 - 3^4 + 8^5 + 9^5 - 6^5$
$82955 := 8^4 + 2^2 + 9^3 + 5^0 + 5^7$	$83636 := 8^5 + 3^6 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 6^6$	$83925 := -8^2 - 3^6 + 9^4 + 2^5 + 5^7$
$82958 := -8^1 + 2^4 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 8^4$	$83650 := -8^2 - 3^7 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 0^1$	$83945 := -8^1 - 3^6 + 9^4 - 4^1 + 5^7$
$82959 := 8^4 + 2^3 + 9^0 + 5^7 + 9^3$	$83651 := -8^2 - 3^7 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 1^0$	$83946 := 8^1 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 6^5$
$82975 := -8^4 - 2^4 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 5^7$	$83652 := -8^2 - 3^7 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 2^1$	$83950 := -8^1 - 3^6 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 0^0$
$83207 := -8^5 - 3^7 + 2^9 + 0^0 + 7^6$	$83653 := -8^2 + 3^1 + 6^5 + 5^7 - 3^7$	$83964 := 8^3 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 4^7$
$83246 := -8^6 - 3^4 - 2^0 + 4^8 + 6^7$	$83654 := -8^2 - 3^7 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 4^1$	$83968 := -8^2 - 3^2 + 9^5 - 6^5 + 8^5$
$83254 := 8^3 + 3^2 + 2^9 + 5^7 + 4^6$	$83654 := 8^5 + 3^2 + 6^6 + 5^3 + 4^6$	$83986 := -8^2 + 3^2 + 9^5 + 8^5 - 6^5$
$83257 := 8^3 + 3^7 + 2^5 + 5^7 + 7^4$	$83655 := -8^2 - 3^7 + 6^5 + 5^1 + 5^7$	$84043 := -8^2 + 4^7 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 3^7$
$83342 := -8^4 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 4^8 + 2^5$	$83656 := -8^2 - 3^7 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 6^5$	$84075 := 8^3 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 7^4 + 5^6$
$83346 := -8^4 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 4^8 + 6^2$	$83657 := -8^1 - 3^7 + 6^5 + 5^7 - 7^2$	$84137 := -8^5 - 4^2 + 1^0 - 3^6 + 7^6$
$83349 := 8^3 + 3^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 9^5$	$83658 := -8^2 - 3^7 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 8^1$	$84159 := -8^3 - 4^2 + 1^0 + 5^7 + 9^4$
$83364 := 8^5 + 3^6 + 3^7 + 6^6 + 4^5$	$83659 := -8^2 - 3^7 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 9^1$	$84243 := 8^1 + 4^7 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 3^7$
$83364 := -8^6 + 3^2 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 4^8$	$83667 := -8^5 + 3^4 - 6^4 + 6^0 + 7^6$	$84257 := -8^5 - 4^0 + 2^1 - 5^4 + 7^6$
$83435 := -8^4 + 3^7 + 4^8 + 3^9 + 5^3$	$83674 := 8^1 + 3^3 + 6^4 + 7^5 + 4^8$	$84279 := -8^5 - 4^0 + 2^7 + 7^6 - 9^3$
$83436 := -8^6 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 6^7$	$83674 := -8^6 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 + 4^8$	$84334 := -8^4 + 4^5 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 4^8$
$83456 := -8^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^7 + 6^4$	$83677 := -8^4 - 3^3 - 6^6 + 7^5 + 7^6$	$84335 := -8^2 + 4^6 - 3^2 + 3^7 + 5^7$
		$84337 := -8^3 + 4^8 - 3^3 + 3^9 - 7^3$
		$84345 := -8^2 + 4^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^7$
		$84352 := -8^2 + 4^6 + 3^7 + 5^7 + 2^3$

$84353 := -8^2 + 4^6 + 3^2 + 5^7 + 3^7$	$84557 := -8^2 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 5^7 + 7^4$	$84750 := -8^5 - 4^4 + 7^6 + 5^3 + 0^1$
$84356 := -8^3 - 4^5 - 3^2 + 5^7 + 6^5$	$84559 := -8^2 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 5^7 + 9^4$	$84751 := -8^5 - 4^1 + 7^6 - 5^3 - 1^0$
$84357 := -8^5 - 4^4 - 3^5 - 5^2 + 7^6$	$84573 := -8^5 - 4^3 - 5^0 + 7^6 - 3^5$	$84752 := -8^5 - 4^2 + 7^6 - 5^4 + 2^9$
$84358 := -8^1 - 4^4 + 3^8 + 5^7 - 8^2$	$84574 := -8^2 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 4^6$	$84753 := -8^5 - 4^1 + 7^6 - 5^3 + 3^0$
$84365 := -8^2 - 4^4 + 3^8 - 6^0 + 5^7$	$84575 := -8^5 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^6 - 5^2$	$84754 := -8^5 - 4^0 + 7^6 - 5^3 - 4^0$
$84367 := -8^5 - 4^0 - 3^6 + 6^3 + 7^6$	$84576 := -8^5 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^6 - 6^3$	$84755 := 8^1 + 4^6 + 7^4 + 5^3 + 5^7$
$84372 := -8^5 + 4^1 - 3^0 + 7^6 - 2^9$	$84577 := -8^5 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^6 - 7^3$	$84755 := -8^5 - 4^4 + 7^6 + 5^1 + 5^3$
$84373 := -8^5 - 4^4 - 3^2 + 7^6 - 3^5$	$84583 := -8^3 + 4^8 - 5^3 + 8^0 + 3^9$	$84756 := -8^5 - 4^0 + 7^6 - 5^3 + 6^0$
$84376 := 8^1 + 4^8 + 3^6 + 7^5 + 6^4$	$84593 := -8^1 - 4^1 + 5^7 - 9^2 + 3^8$	$84757 := 8^1 + 4^8 + 7^4 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$84376 := -8^5 - 4^4 - 3^5 + 7^6 - 6^1$	$84596 := -8^3 - 4^3 + 5^7 - 9^3 + 6^5$	$84757 := -8^5 - 4^4 + 7^1 + 5^3 + 7^6$
$84377 := -8^5 + 4^7 - 3^4 + 7^6 - 7^5$	$84597 := -8^3 - 4^7 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$84758 := -8^2 - 4^3 + 7^6 + 5^1 - 8^5$
$84378 := -8^3 - 4^8 + 3^2 + 7^6 + 8^5$	$84598 := -8^1 - 4^2 + 5^7 + 9^4 - 8^2$	$84759 := 8^1 + 4^2 + 7^2 + 5^7 + 9^4$
$84379 := -8^5 - 4^2 + 3^5 + 7^6 - 9^3$	$84626 := -8^6 + 4^8 + 6^4 + 2^1 + 6^7$	$84759 := -8^5 - 4^2 + 7^6 - 5^2 - 9^2$
$84394 := -8^4 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 9^4 + 4^8$	$84627 := -8^5 - 4^1 + 6^1 - 2^8 + 7^6$	$84763 := -8^5 - 4^0 + 7^6 - 6^2 - 3^4$
$84395 := -8^1 - 4^4 - 3^3 + 9^4 + 5^7$	$84637 := -8^5 - 4^0 - 6^3 - 3^3 + 7^6$	$84767 := -8^5 - 4^3 - 7^2 - 6^0 + 7^6$
$84443 := -8^1 + 4^4 - 4^5 + 4^8 + 3^9$	$84647 := -8^5 - 4^4 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 7^6$	$84772 := -8^5 + 4^1 - 7^2 + 7^6 - 2^6$
$84449 := -8^4 + 4^3 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 9^4$	$84659 := -8^2 + 4^0 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 9^4$	$84783 := -8^5 - 4^2 + 7^6 - 8^0 - 3^4$
$84530 := -8^2 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 3^9 + 0^1$	$84667 := -8^5 + 4^0 - 6^3 + 6^0 + 7^6$	$84792 := -8^4 + 4^8 + 7^5 + 9^4 - 2^4$
$84531 := -8^2 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 3^9 + 1^0$	$84670 := -8^5 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 7^6 + 0^0$	$84793 := -8^5 - 4^1 + 7^6 - 9^2 - 3^1$
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$84536 := -8^2 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 3^9 + 6^1$	$84732 := -8^3 + 4^8 - 7^1 + 3^9 + 2^5$	$84817 := -8^2 - 4^0 - 8^5 + 1^0 + 7^6$
$84537 := -8^1 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 3^9 - 7^2$	$84733 := -8^3 + 4^8 - 7^0 + 3^3 + 3^9$	$84827 := -8^5 - 4^3 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 7^6$
$84538 := -8^2 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 3^9 + 8^1$	$84735 := -8^1 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 3^8 + 5^7$	$84837 := -8^5 - 4^2 - 8^0 - 3^3 + 7^6$
$84539 := -8^2 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$84736 := -8^3 + 4^8 - 7^1 + 3^9 + 6^2$	$84864 := -8^6 + 4^5 + 8^3 + 6^7 + 4^8$
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$84553 := -8^2 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 5^7 + 3^8$	$84739 := -8^3 + 4^8 - 7^2 + 3^9 + 9^2$	$84870 := -8^1 - 4^1 - 8^5 + 7^6 + 0^0$
		$84871 := -8^1 - 4^0 - 8^5 + 7^6 - 1^0$
		$84872 := -8^1 + 4^0 - 8^5 + 7^6 - 2^1$
		$84873 := -8^1 + 4^0 - 8^5 + 7^6 - 3^0$

$84873 := -8^1 - 4^0 - 8^5 + 7^6 + 3^0$	$84973 := -8^5 - 4^2 + 9^2 + 7^6 + 3^3$	$85264 := 8^4 + 5^6 + 2^0 + 6^1 + 4^8$
$84874 := -8^1 + 4^0 + 8^5 + 7^6 - 4^8$	$84974 := -8^5 - 4^1 + 9^2 + 7^6 + 4^2$	$85265 := -8^3 - 5^3 + 2^0 + 6^5 + 5^7$
$84875 := -8^1 + 4^0 - 8^5 + 7^6 + 5^0$	$84977 := -8^5 + 4^2 + 9^2 + 7^6 - 7^0$	$85267 := -8^5 - 5^3 + 2^9 - 6^0 + 7^6$
$84876 := -8^1 + 4^1 - 8^5 + 7^6 - 6^0$	$84979 := -8^5 + 4^2 + 9^0 + 7^6 + 9^2$	$85272 := -8^5 - 5^3 + 2^2 + 7^6 + 2^9$
$84877 := -8^5 - 4^1 + 8^0 - 7^0 + 7^6$	$84993 := -8^5 - 4^4 + 9^5 + 9^5 - 3^4$	$85274 := 8^4 + 5^6 + 2^4 + 7^0 + 4^8$
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$84878 := -8^1 + 4^1 + 8^0 + 7^6 - 8^5$	$85037 := 8^1 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 7^3$	$85279 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 7^2 + 9^4$
$84879 := -8^5 - 4^0 + 8^1 + 7^6 - 9^1$	$85163 := -8^1 + 5^7 - 1^0 + 6^5 - 3^6$	$85294 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 9^4 + 4^3$
$84887 := -8^5 - 4^0 - 8^0 + 8^1 + 7^6$	$85189 := -8^1 + 5^7 - 1^0 + 8^3 + 9^4$	$85294 := -8^6 + 5^7 + 2^4 + 9^6 - 4^9$
$84897 := -8^2 - 4^0 - 8^5 + 9^2 + 7^6$	$85203 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 2^2 + 0^0 + 3^8$	$85295 := -8^1 + 5^4 - 2^3 + 9^4 + 5^7$
$84907 := -8^5 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 0^0 + 7^6$	$85230 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 0^1$	$85299 := -8^5 + 5^0 - 2^5 + 9^5 + 9^5$
$84927 := -8^5 - 4^0 - 9^2 + 2^7 + 7^6$	$85231 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 1^0$	$85324 := 8^2 + 5^2 + 3^9 + 2^4 + 4^8$
$84935 := -8^1 + 4^4 + 9^0 + 3^8 + 5^7$	$85232 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 2^5$	$85325 := 8^3 + 5^3 + 3^8 + 2^1 + 5^7$
$84937 := -8^3 + 4^9 - 9^5 + 3^1 - 7^6$	$85233 := 8^1 + 5^7 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 3^8$	$85327 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 2^7 + 7^0$
$84938 := -8^2 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 3^9 + 8^3$	$85234 := 8^1 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^8$	$85327 := -8^5 + 5^4 - 3^5 + 2^6 + 7^6$
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$84950 := 8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 0^1$	$85235 := 8^3 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^7$	$85342 := -8^1 - 5^3 + 3^9 + 4^8 + 2^8$
$84951 := 8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 1^0$	$85236 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^2$	$85342 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 2^7$
$84952 := 8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 2^1$	$85237 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 7^1$	$85343 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 3^8$
$84953 := 8^1 + 4^2 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 3^5$	$85237 := -8^5 + 5^4 - 2^9 + 3^5 + 7^6$	$85344 := -8^2 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 4^8$
$84954 := 8^1 + 4^1 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 4^4$	$85238 := 8^1 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 8^3$	$85344 := 8^5 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 4^7$
$84955 := 8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 5^7$	$85239 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 9^4$	$85346 := -8^2 - 5^2 + 3^9 + 4^8 + 6^3$
$84956 := 8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 6^1$	$85248 := -8^1 + 5^6 - 2^0 + 4^8 + 8^4$	$85348 := 8^2 + 5^0 + 3^9 + 4^8 + 8^2$
$84957 := 8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 7^1$	$85256 := -8^1 - 5^3 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 6^5$	$85348 := -8^5 + 5^9 - 3^0 + 4^9 - 8^7$
$84957 := -8^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 7^3$	$85257 := -8^5 - 5^1 + 2^8 + 5^3 + 7^6$	$85350 := 8^4 + 5^5 + 3^1 + 5^7 + 0^0$
$84958 := 8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^7 + 8^1$	$85259 := -8^2 + 5^3 + 2^9 + 5^7 + 9^4$	$85356 := 8^4 + 5^5 + 3^2 + 5^7 + 6^0$
$84959 := 8^1 + 4^4 + 9^1 + 5^7 + 9^4$	$85260 := -8^3 + 5^7 - 2^7 + 6^5 - 0^0$	$85361 := -8^3 + 5^7 - 3^3 + 6^5 - 1^0$
$84959 := -8^2 + 4^4 + 9^2 + 5^7 + 9^4$	$85262 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 2^0 + 6^5 - 2^7$	$85362 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 2^7$
$84967 := -8^5 - 4^0 + 9^2 + 6^1 + 7^6$	$85263 := 8^2 + 5^7 + 2^9 + 6^0 + 3^8$	$85363 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 3^0 + 6^5 - 3^3$
		$85364 := -8^2 + 5^7 - 3^6 + 6^5 + 4^4$
		$85365 := -8^3 - 5^2 + 3^0 + 6^5 + 5^7$
		$85367 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 3^3 + 6^5 - 7^2$

$85387 := -8^5 - 5^1 - 3^0 + 8^3 + 7^6$	$85654 := -8^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 5^7 - 4^4$	$85963 := -8^2 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 6^6 - 3^9$
$85406 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 4^2 + 0^0 + 6^5$	$85659 := -8^4 + 5^5 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 9^3$	$85963 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 6^2 + 3^8$
$85432 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 4^6 + 3^7 + 2^9$	$85667 := -8^3 - 5^7 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 7^6$	$85967 := 8^1 + 5^7 + 9^1 + 6^5 + 7^2$
$85433 := 8^1 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 3^4 + 3^9$	$85672 := -8^3 - 5^7 + 6^6 + 7^6 + 2^2$	$85967 := -8^1 + 5^7 + 9^2 + 6^5 - 7^1$
$85435 := 8^1 + 5^5 + 4^6 + 3^4 + 5^7$	$85675 := 8^5 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 5^5$	$85968 := -8^4 - 5^8 + 9^6 - 6^6 - 8^4$
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$85439 := 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^2 + 3^6 + 9^4$	$85693 := -8^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 + 9^5 - 3^6$	$86135 := -8^1 + 6^5 - 1^0 + 3^5 + 5^7$
$85456 := -8^2 - 5^3 - 4^4 + 5^7 + 6^5$	$85724 := -8^5 - 5^5 + 7^6 - 2^7 + 4^6$	$86153 := 8^1 + 6^5 + 1^0 + 5^7 + 3^5$
$85459 := 8^3 + 5^1 + 4^4 + 5^7 + 9^4$	$85726 := -8^5 + 5^4 + 7^6 + 2^2 + 6^3$	$86172 := -8^5 + 6^4 - 1^0 + 7^6 - 2^2$
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$85473 := -8^2 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 7^3 + 3^9$	$85736 := -8^5 + 5^3 + 7^6 + 3^6 + 6^0$	$86174 := -8^5 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 7^6 - 4^1$
$85474 := -8^5 + 5^4 - 4^2 + 7^6 - 4^2$	$85743 := 8^3 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 3^9$	$86175 := -8^5 + 6^4 - 1^0 + 7^6 - 5^0$
$85476 := -8^3 + 5^7 - 4^4 + 7^3 + 6^5$	$85747 := -8^2 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 4^8 + 7^5$	$86177 := -8^5 + 6^4 - 1^0 + 7^0 + 7^6$
$85477 := 8^1 + 5^5 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 7^5$	$85763 := -8^1 + 5^7 - 7^2 + 6^5 - 3^4$	$86179 := -8^5 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 7^6 + 9^0$
$85479 := -8^5 + 5^3 - 4^4 + 7^6 + 9^3$	$85766 := -8^1 + 5^7 - 7^3 + 6^3 + 6^5$	$86225 := 8^2 + 6^5 + 2^2 + 2^8 + 5^7$
$85507 := -8^5 + 5^0 + 5^4 + 0^1 + 7^6$	$85786 := -8^5 + 5^4 + 7^6 + 8^2 + 6^3$	$86243 := 8^5 + 6^6 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 3^8$
$85526 := -8^3 + 5^6 + 5^7 + 2^6 - 6^5$	$85788 := -8^2 - 5^5 + 7^6 + 8^4 - 8^5$	$86249 := 8^5 + 6^6 + 2^3 + 4^4 + 9^4$
$85527 := -8^5 + 5^1 + 5^4 + 2^4 + 7^6$	$85835 := 8^3 + 5^3 + 8^3 + 3^8 + 5^7$	$86285 := 8^2 + 6^5 + 2^8 + 8^2 + 5^7$
$85547 := -8^5 + 5^2 + 5^4 + 4^2 + 7^6$	$85846 := -8^2 + 5^7 + 8^1 + 4^0 + 6^5$	$86285 := -8^2 + 6^5 - 2^6 + 8^3 + 5^7$
$85563 := 8^4 + 5^5 + 5^7 + 6^3 + 3^0$	$85857 := -8^5 - 5^5 + 8^4 + 5^1 + 7^6$	$86337 := -8^4 - 6^5 + 3^5 - 3^9 + 7^6$
$85564 := -8^4 + 5^6 + 5^7 + 6^1 - 4^6$	$85859 := 8^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 + 5^7 + 9^0$	$86337 := 8^5 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 3^8 + 7^3$
$85567 := -8^5 + 5^2 + 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^6$	$85862 := -8^1 + 5^7 + 8^0 + 6^5 - 2^5$	$86345 := 8^4 + 6^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^7$
$85606 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 6^3 + 0^0 + 6^5$	$85863 := -8^2 + 5^7 - 8^0 + 6^5 + 3^3$	$86352 := -8^2 + 6^5 + 3^1 + 5^7 + 2^9$
$85631 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 6^5 + 3^5 - 1^0$	$85886 := -8^1 + 5^7 - 8^1 + 8^0 + 6^5$	$86353 := 8^5 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 5^3 + 3^8$
$85633 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 6^5 + 3^0 + 3^5$	$85896 := -8^2 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^4 + 6^6$	$86354 := 8^4 + 6^2 + 3^0 + 5^7 + 4^6$
$85639 := 8^1 + 5^7 + 6^3 + 3^6 + 9^4$	$85926 := 8^1 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 6^5$	$86358 := -8^2 + 6^5 + 3^2 + 5^7 + 8^3$
$85644 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 6^5 + 4^4 - 4^0$	$85926 := -8^1 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 2^5 + 6^5$	$86373 := 8^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 7^3 + 3^9$
$85646 := -8^3 + 5^7 + 6^0 + 4^4 + 6^5$	$85929 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 2^1 + 9^4$	$86374 := -8^5 + 6^5 - 3^7 + 7^6 - 4^6$
$85647 := 8^4 + 5^7 + 6^0 + 4^5 + 7^4$	$85943 := 8^3 + 5^7 + 9^3 + 4^2 + 3^8$	$86377 := 8^5 + 6^6 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 7^3$
		$86395 := -8^4 - 6^6 - 3^3 + 9^5 + 5^7$
		$86398 := -8^4 - 6^4 - 3^3 + 9^5 + 8^5$
		$86415 := 8^3 + 6^5 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 5^7$

$86425 := 8^1 + 6^5 + 4^1 + 2^9 + 5^7$	$86665 := 8^3 + 6^2 + 6^3 + 6^5 + 5^7$	$87454 := 8^1 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 4^8$
$86428 := -8^4 - 6^5 + 4^8 - 2^2 + 8^5$	$86684 := -8^3 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 8^5 - 4^1$	$87455 := -8^4 + 7^5 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 5^5$
$86443 := -8^1 + 6^4 - 4^3 + 4^8 + 3^9$	$86687 := -8^3 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 8^5 - 7^0$	$87464 := 8^4 + 7^5 + 4^5 + 6^0 + 4^8$
$86445 := -8^1 + 6^7 - 4^9 + 4^8 + 5^5$	$86689 := -8^3 + 6^5 + 6^6 + 8^5 + 9^0$	$87474 := -8^5 + 7^4 - 4^3 + 7^6 + 4^4$
$86445 := 8^3 + 6^5 + 4^2 + 4^2 + 5^7$	$86695 := 8^2 + 6^0 + 6^5 + 9^3 + 5^7$	$87589 := -8^4 - 7^1 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^5$
$86448 := -8^4 - 6^5 + 4^2 + 4^8 + 8^5$	$86757 := 8^3 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 7^3$	$87598 := -8^5 - 7^5 + 5^7 + 9^5 - 8^0$
$86452 := -8^6 + 6^7 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 2^0$	$86907 := -8^5 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 0^0 + 7^6$	$87634 := 8^1 + 7^4 + 6^1 + 3^9 + 4^8$
$86454 := -8^6 + 6^7 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 4^8$	$86935 := -8^4 - 6^3 + 9^4 + 3^8 + 5^7$	$87635 := 8^3 + 7^4 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 5^7$
$86465 := -8^2 - 6^5 - 4^7 - 6^7 + 5^8$	$86998 := -8^4 + 6^1 - 9^3 + 9^5 + 8^5$	$87657 := -8^5 - 7^3 - 6^1 + 5^5 + 7^6$
$86465 := 8^3 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 6^5 + 5^7$	$87095 := 8^1 + 7^4 + 0^1 + 9^4 + 5^7$	$87674 := -8^5 - 7^1 - 6^4 + 7^6 + 4^6$
$86468 := -8^4 - 6^5 + 4^8 + 6^2 + 8^5$	$87237 := -8^5 - 7^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^6$	$87680 := -8^5 + 7^6 - 6^4 + 8^4 - 0^0$
$86472 := 8^4 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 7^5 + 2^5$	$87255 := -8^4 - 7^4 + 2^1 + 5^6 + 5^7$	$87682 := -8^5 + 7^6 - 6^4 + 8^4 + 2^0$
$86476 := 8^4 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 7^5 + 6^2$	$87267 := -8^5 + 7^4 - 2^4 + 6^0 + 7^6$	$87763 := -8^3 - 7^4 + 7^6 - 6^6 + 3^9$
$86485 := 8^1 + 6^5 + 4^3 + 8^3 + 5^7$	$87272 := -8^5 + 7^4 - 2^1 + 7^6 - 2^3$	$87787 := -8^5 - 7^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 7^6$
$86489 := -8^4 - 6^4 + 4^3 + 8^5 + 9^5$	$87273 := -8^5 + 7^4 - 2^3 + 7^6 - 3^0$	$87836 := 8^5 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 6^3$
$86495 := 8^3 + 6^4 + 4^0 + 9^4 + 5^7$	$87274 := -8^5 + 7^4 - 2^2 + 7^6 - 4^1$	$87895 := -8^4 + 7^2 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 5^3$
$86498 := 8^3 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 9^4 + 8^5$	$87275 := -8^5 + 7^4 - 2^1 + 7^6 - 5^1$	$87928 := -8^4 - 7^2 + 9^5 + 2^8 + 8^5$
$86534 := 8^4 + 6^3 + 5^7 + 3^0 + 4^6$	$87277 := -8^5 - 7^0 - 2^2 + 7^4 + 7^6$	$87944 := -8^5 + 7^6 - 9^1 + 4^6 - 4^5$
$86534 := -8^6 + 6^7 + 5^5 + 3^4 + 4^8$	$87278 := -8^1 + 7^4 + 2^2 + 7^6 - 8^5$	$87983 := -8^4 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 8^5 - 3^4$
$86535 := 8^1 + 6^5 + 5^4 + 3^0 + 5^7$	$87279 := -8^5 + 7^4 - 2^1 + 7^6 - 9^0$	$87984 := -8^4 + 7^1 + 9^5 + 8^5 + 4^4$
$86535 := -8^5 + 6^8 + 5^8 + 3^7 - 5^9$	$87287 := -8^5 + 7^4 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 7^6$	$87986 := -8^4 + 7^2 + 9^5 + 8^5 + 6^3$
$86542 := 8^3 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 4^0 + 2^7$	$87309 := -8^4 + 7^6 - 3^9 + 0^1 - 9^4$	$88229 := -8^4 + 8^5 - 2^2 + 2^9 + 9^5$
$86554 := 8^3 + 6^5 + 5^3 + 5^7 + 4^2$	$87322 := -8^5 + 7^6 + 3^7 + 2^8 - 2^1$	$88249 := -8^4 + 8^5 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^5$
$86558 := 8^4 + 6^3 + 5^2 + 5^7 + 8^4$	$87323 := -8^5 + 7^6 - 3^0 + 2^8 + 3^7$	$88269 := -8^4 + 8^5 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^5$
$86573 := -8^2 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 7^1 + 3^6$	$87324 := -8^5 + 7^6 + 3^7 + 2^9 - 4^4$	$88345 := 8^5 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 5^5$
$86593 := -8^2 - 6^3 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 3^7$	$87325 := -8^5 + 7^6 + 3^7 + 2^8 + 5^0$	$88352 := 8^5 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 5^5 + 2^3$
$86645 := -8^2 - 6^3 + 6^5 + 4^5 + 5^7$	$87343 := -8^2 + 7^0 + 3^7 + 4^8 + 3^9$	$88353 := 8^5 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 3^9$
$86645 := 8^3 + 6^3 + 6^5 + 4^2 + 5^7$	$87347 := -8^5 + 7^4 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 7^6$	$88365 := -8^4 - 8^0 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 5^7$
$86648 := -8^4 + 6^3 - 6^5 + 4^8 + 8^5$	$87435 := -8^3 - 7^0 + 4^7 - 3^8 + 5^7$	$88489 := 8^1 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 8^5 + 9^4$
		$88489 := -8^4 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 8^5 + 9^5$
		$88536 := -8^2 + 8^3 + 5^7 + 3^7 + 6^5$

$88559 := -8^5 + 8^6 - 5^0 + 5^8 - 9^6$	$89856 := -8^5 - 9^6 + 8^6 + 5^8 + 6^4$	$92348 := 9^5 + 2^5 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 8^5$
$88722 := -8^5 + 8^4 + 7^6 + 2^0 - 2^8$	$89963 := -8^6 + 9^4 + 9^5 + 6^7 + 3^8$	$92364 := -9^2 - 2^6 - 3^9 + 6^6 + 4^8$
$88793 := -8^4 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 9^5 + 3^6$	$90754 := -9^2 - 0^0 + 7^5 + 5^7 - 4^6$	$92365 := -9^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 6^5 + 5^7$
$88794 := -8^4 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 9^5 + 4^5$	$91089 := -9^3 + 1^0 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 9^5$	$92366 := -9^3 + 2^9 - 3^6 + 6^6 + 6^6$
$88972 := -8^5 + 8^4 - 9^0 + 7^6 - 2^2$	$91372 := -9^4 - 1^0 - 3^9 + 7^6 - 2^5$	$92368 := 9^5 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 6^2 + 8^5$
$88973 := -8^5 + 8^4 - 9^0 + 7^6 - 3^1$	$91378 := -9^5 + 1^0 + 3^2 + 7^6 + 8^5$	$92383 := 9^5 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 3^3$
$88974 := -8^5 + 8^4 + 9^0 + 7^6 - 4^1$	$91538 := -9^5 - 1^0 - 5^9 + 3^8 + 8^7$	$92387 := 9^5 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 8^5 + 7^2$
$88975 := -8^5 + 8^4 - 9^0 + 7^6 - 5^0$	$91553 := -9^1 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 5^7 - 3^7$	$92388 := 9^5 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 8^3 + 8^5$
$88977 := -8^2 - 8^5 + 9^4 - 7^4 + 7^6$	$91809 := -9^1 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 0^1 + 9^5$	$92436 := -9^1 - 2^6 + 4^8 - 3^9 + 6^6$
$88978 := -8^1 + 8^4 + 9^1 + 7^6 - 8^5$	$91820 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^0 + 0^0$	$92454 := 9^5 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 4^7$
$88979 := -8^5 + 8^4 + 9^0 + 7^6 + 9^0$	$91821 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 1^0$	$92458 := 9^5 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^5$
$88987 := -8^5 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 8^4 + 7^6$	$91822 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 2^1$	$92465 := 9^4 + 2^1 + 4^0 + 6^5 + 5^7$
$89295 := 8^4 + 9^0 + 2^9 + 9^4 + 5^7$	$91823 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 3^1$	$92475 := -9^4 + 2^3 + 4^6 + 7^5 + 5^7$
$89298 := -8^5 + 9^5 - 2^7 + 9^5 + 8^4$	$91824 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 4^1$	$92497 := 9^5 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 9^0 + 7^5$
$89324 := 8^4 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 2^3 + 4^8$	$91825 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 5^1$	$92525 := -9^3 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 2^4 + 5^7$
$89343 := 8^4 + 9^0 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 3^9$	$91826 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 6^1$	$92526 := 9^4 + 2^5 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 6^5$
$89365 := -8^6 + 9^1 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 5^7$	$91827 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 7^1$	$92566 := -9^3 + 2^3 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 6^6$
$89390 := 8^4 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 0^0$	$91828 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 8^5$	$92582 := 9^5 + 2^7 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 2^9$
$89417 := 8^3 + 9^4 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 7^5$	$91829 := 9^1 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 9^5$	$92583 := 9^5 + 2^5 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 3^6$
$89417 := -8^5 + 9^5 + 4^8 + 1^0 - 7^4$	$91842 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 2^3$	$92616 := -9^3 + 2^5 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 6^6$
$89478 := -8^2 - 9^5 + 4^6 - 7^6 + 8^6$	$91843 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 3^2$	$92637 := -9^4 - 2^6 + 6^4 - 3^9 + 7^6$
$89497 := 8^3 + 9^2 + 4^8 + 9^4 + 7^5$	$91862 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 2^3$	$92646 := -9^3 - 2^0 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 6^6$
$89497 := -8^5 + 9^2 + 4^8 + 9^5 - 7^4$	$91863 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^2$	$92654 := 9^4 + 2^7 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 4^3$
$89525 := -8^4 - 9^0 + 5^6 - 2^7 + 5^7$	$91883 := 9^5 + 1^0 + 8^2 + 8^5 + 3^0$	$92663 := -9^3 - 2^0 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 3^4$
$89564 := -8^3 + 9^5 - 5^6 + 6^6 - 4^1$	$92082 := 9^5 + 2^3 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 2^8$	$92677 := 9^5 + 2^3 + 6^1 + 7^5 + 7^5$
$89567 := -8^2 - 9^5 - 5^6 + 6^6 + 7^6$	$92083 := 9^5 + 2^8 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 3^2$	$92678 := 9^5 + 2^9 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 8^5$
$89569 := -8^3 + 9^0 - 5^6 + 6^6 + 9^5$	$92274 := 9^5 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$92696 := -9^3 + 2^5 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 6^6$
$89584 := -8^5 - 9^6 + 5^8 + 8^6 + 4^5$	$92324 := 9^4 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 2^9 + 4^8$	$92727 := 9^5 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 2^5 + 7^5$
$89834 := -8^4 - 9^4 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 4^8$	$92345 := -9^1 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 4^7 + 5^7$	$92735 := -9^1 - 2^0 + 7^5 - 3^7 + 5^7$
		$92784 := 9^5 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 4^7$
		$92803 := 9^5 + 2^8 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 3^6$
		$92834 := 9^5 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 3^6 + 4^4$

$92842 := 9^5 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 2^9$	$93559 := 9^4 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 5^7 + 9^4$	$94253 := -9^1 + 4^7 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 3^5$
$92843 := 9^5 + 2^0 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 3^0$	$93574 := -9^5 + 3^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 4^8$	$94256 := -9^2 - 4^7 + 2^5 + 5^8 - 6^7$
$92844 := 9^5 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 4^5$	$93575 := -9^3 - 3^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 5^7$	$94273 := -9^4 - 4^7 - 2^9 + 7^6 + 3^4$
$92846 := 9^5 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 6^0$	$93577 := -9^3 - 3^8 + 5^2 - 7^5 + 7^6$	$94275 := -9^2 - 4^3 - 2^9 + 7^5 + 5^7$
$92854 := 9^5 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 4^5$	$93628 := 9^5 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 2^9 + 8^5$	$94277 := -9^4 + 4^1 - 2^3 + 7^6 - 7^5$
$92874 := 9^5 + 2^5 + 8^5 + 7^0 + 4^5$	$93643 := -9^2 + 3^6 + 6^5 + 4^8 + 3^9$	$94347 := 9^5 + 4^7 + 3^7 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$92896 := -9^3 + 2^9 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 6^4$	$93645 := -9^3 + 3^4 - 6^3 + 4^7 + 5^7$	$94359 := 9^5 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 5^6 + 9^0$
$92897 := 9^3 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 7^3$	$93662 := -9^2 - 3^4 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 2^9$	$94385 := 9^5 + 4^4 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 5^3$
$92965 := -9^1 + 2^9 + 9^4 + 6^5 + 5^7$	$93663 := 9^2 + 3^3 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 3^5$	$94387 := -9^4 + 4^8 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 7^4$
$92966 := -9^1 - 2^8 - 9^2 + 6^6 + 6^6$	$93665 := -9^1 - 3^1 + 6^5 + 6^5 + 5^7$	$94425 := -9^2 - 4^0 + 4^7 - 2^1 + 5^7$
$92968 := -9^2 - 2^6 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$93667 := 9^1 + 3^1 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 7^3$	$94435 := -9^1 - 4^3 + 4^7 - 3^0 + 5^7$
$92984 := -9^4 + 2^9 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 4^8$	$93754 := -9^3 - 3^3 + 7^0 + 5^7 + 4^7$	$94437 := 9^4 + 4^4 + 4^8 + 3^9 + 7^4$
$93069 := 9^4 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 9^5$	$93772 := -9^4 + 3^1 - 7^5 + 7^6 - 2^9$	$94445 := -9^2 + 4^0 + 4^2 + 4^7 + 5^7$
$93084 := 9^5 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 4^5$	$93778 := -9^4 + 3^2 - 7^5 + 7^6 - 8^3$	$94447 := -9^4 - 4^0 - 4^4 - 4^7 + 7^6$
$93266 := -9^1 + 3^3 - 2^6 + 6^6 + 6^6$	$93788 := -9^2 - 3^9 + 7^6 - 8^0 - 8^4$	$94452 := -9^1 - 4^2 + 4^7 + 5^7 - 2^5$
$93268 := 9^5 + 3^3 + 2^7 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$93797 := -9^1 - 3^9 + 7^4 - 9^4 + 7^6$	$94453 := -9^2 + 4^2 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 3^2$
$93275 := -9^4 - 3^7 - 2^0 + 7^6 - 5^6$	$93798 := -9^2 - 3^9 + 7^6 + 9^1 - 8^4$	$94456 := -9^2 + 4^3 + 4^7 + 5^7 - 6^2$
$93283 := 9^5 + 3^6 + 2^3 + 8^5 + 3^6$	$93845 := -9^3 + 3^0 + 8^2 + 4^7 + 5^7$	$94465 := -9^2 + 4^0 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 5^7$
$93353 := -9^2 - 3^7 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 3^9$	$93846 := 9^5 + 3^6 + 8^5 + 4^1 + 6^4$	$94474 := 9^5 + 4^4 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 4^7$
$93357 := -9^4 - 3^7 + 3^4 - 5^6 + 7^6$	$93849 := -9^2 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 4^8 - 9^4$	$94475 := -9^3 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 5^7$
$93376 := -9^4 + 3^7 - 3^9 + 7^6 - 6^3$	$93867 := -9^1 - 3^9 - 8^4 + 6^1 + 7^6$	$94478 := 9^5 + 4^1 + 4^4 + 7^4 + 8^5$
$93426 := -9^2 + 3^9 + 4^8 + 2^9 + 6^5$	$93868 := 9^5 + 3^5 + 8^3 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$94485 := -9^1 - 4^2 + 4^7 + 8^0 + 5^7$
$93435 := 9^4 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 3^8 + 5^7$	$93869 := 9^3 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 9^5$	$94495 := -9^1 - 4^1 + 4^7 - 9^0 + 5^7$
$93435 := -9^4 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 5^7$	$93884 := -9^2 - 3^5 - 8^4 + 8^5 + 4^8$	$94500 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 0^0 - 0^0$
$93466 := 9^1 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 6^6 + 6^6$	$93955 := -9^3 + 3^9 + 9^0 + 5^7 - 5^5$	$94501 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 1^0$
$93475 := -9^3 - 3^6 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 5^7$	$93974 := -9^3 - 3^0 - 9^4 + 7^6 - 4^7$	$94502 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 2^0$
$93488 := -9^3 + 3^2 + 4^8 + 8^5 - 8^4$	$94236 := 9^3 + 4^8 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 6^5$	$94503 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 3^1$
$93489 := -9^2 + 3^6 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 9^5$	$94245 := -9^1 + 4^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 5^7$	$94504 := -9^1 + 4^1 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 4^7$
$93534 := -9^3 - 3^1 + 5^7 - 3^5 + 4^7$	$94252 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 5^7 - 2^8$	$94505 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 5^7$
		$94506 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 6^1$
		$94507 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 7^1$
		$94508 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 8^1$

$94509 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 9^1$	$94592 := 9^2 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 2^0$	$94726 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 2^4 + 6^1$
$94520 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^0 + 0^0$	$94635 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 3^4 + 5^7$	$94727 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^1 + 2^4 + 7^6$
$94521 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 1^0$	$94635 := -9^2 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 3^5 + 5^7$	$94728 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 2^4 + 8^1$
$94522 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 2^1$	$94645 := -9^2 + 4^0 + 6^3 + 4^7 + 5^7$	$94729 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 2^4 + 9^1$
$94523 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 3^1$	$94652 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 2^7$	$94730 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 3^3 - 0^0$
$94523 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^5 - 3^2$	$94652 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 5^7 - 2^6$	$94732 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 3^3 + 2^0$
$94524 := 9^1 + 4^1 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7$	$94653 := 9^2 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 3^3$	$94745 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 4^2 + 5^2$
$94524 := -9^1 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 2^3 + 4^7$	$94653 := -9^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 5^7 + 3^2$	$94762 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 - 6^1 + 2^6$
$94525 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 5^7$	$94657 := -9^3 + 4^8 + 6^6 + 5^0 - 7^5$	$94765 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 6^3 + 5^7$
$94526 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 6^1$	$94667 := -9^4 - 4^7 - 6^0 - 6^2 + 7^6$	$94784 := -9^4 + 4^2 + 7^6 + 8^2 - 4^7$
$94526 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^5 - 6^1$	$94672 := -9^4 - 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^6 + 2^2$	$94852 := -9^4 + 4^8 + 8^5 + 5^5 - 2^4$
$94527 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 7^1$	$94673 := -9^5 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^6 + 3^9$	$94854 := 9^2 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^7$
$94528 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 8^1$	$94675 := 9^2 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^2 + 5^7$	$94859 := -9^1 + 4^8 + 8^5 + 5^5 - 9^4$
$94529 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 9^1$	$94675 := -9^3 + 4^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 5^7$	$94873 := -9^4 + 4^8 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 3^6$
$94542 := 9^1 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 2^3$	$94677 := 9^5 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 + 7^5$	$94875 := -9^1 + 4^2 - 8^2 + 7^5 + 5^7$
$94543 := 9^1 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 3^2$	$94696 := -9^6 + 4^8 + 6^7 + 9^3 + 6^7$	$94894 := -9^5 - 4^7 - 8^5 - 9^5 + 4^9$
$94543 := -9^1 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 3^3$	$94697 := -9^4 - 4^7 - 6^1 - 9^0 + 7^6$	$94947 := 9^3 + 4^7 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$94548 := -9^1 - 4^2 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 8^2$	$94702 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 - 0^0 - 2^0$	$94985 := -9^3 - 4^9 + 9^0 - 8^5 + 5^8$
$94552 := -9^2 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 5^7 - 2^0$	$94703 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 0^1 - 3^0$	$95054 := -9^2 + 5^4 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 4^7$
$94554 := -9^2 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 5^7 + 4^7$	$94704 := -9^4 - 4^0 + 7^6 + 0^0 - 4^7$	$95056 := 9^1 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 6^4$
$94562 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 6^2 + 2^3$	$94705 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 0^1 + 5^0$	$95056 := -9^1 - 5^6 + 0^0 + 5^8 - 6^7$
$94562 := -9^2 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 6^1 + 2^7$	$94706 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 0^0 + 6^0$	$95067 := -9^2 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$
$94563 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 6^2 + 3^2$	$94720 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 2^4 + 0^1$	$95078 := 9^2 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 8^2$
$94563 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 6^2 + 3^3$	$94721 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 2^4 + 1^0$	$95207 := -9^4 - 5^6 - 2^8 + 0^1 + 7^6$
$94567 := -9^2 - 4^7 + 5^8 - 6^7 + 7^3$	$94722 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 + 2^1 + 2^4$	$95227 := -9^3 + 5^7 + 2^9 + 2^9 + 7^5$
$94578 := -9^4 - 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^6 - 8^0$	$94723 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 - 2^3 + 3^3$	$95240 := 9^3 + 5^7 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 0^0$
$94583 := 9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 8^2 + 3^0$	$94724 := -9^4 + 4^1 + 7^6 + 2^4 - 4^7$	$95241 := 9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 1^0$
$94587 := -9^2 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 8^1 + 7^5$	$94725 := 9^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 2^7 + 5^7$	$95242 := 9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 2^1$
$94589 := -9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 8^1 + 9^2$	$94725 := -9^4 - 4^7 + 7^6 - 2^2 + 5^2$	$95243 := 9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 3^1$
		$95244 := 9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 4^7$
		$95245 := 9^3 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^7$
		$95246 := 9^1 + 5^7 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^3$

$95247 := 9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^1$	$95472 := -9^4 - 5^6 + 4^0 + 7^6 + 2^3$	$95795 := 9^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 5^7$
$95248 := 9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 8^1$	$95473 := -9^4 - 5^6 + 4^0 + 7^6 + 3^2$	$95796 := -9^2 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 9^3 + 6^3$
$95249 := 9^1 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 9^3$	$95475 := -9^2 + 5^4 - 4^0 + 7^5 + 5^7$	$95797 := 9^1 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 9^5 + 7^5$
$95258 := -9^1 - 5^6 - 2^0 + 5^7 + 8^5$	$95478 := -9^4 - 5^6 + 4^2 + 7^6 - 8^0$	$95797 := -9^1 - 5^6 + 7^3 - 9^4 + 7^6$
$95267 := -9^1 + 5^7 + 2^7 + 6^3 + 7^5$	$95483 := -9^1 - 5^4 + 4^8 + 8^5 - 3^7$	$95844 := -9^4 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 4^8$
$95270 := 9^2 + 5^7 + 2^8 + 7^5 + 0^0$	$95487 := -9^4 - 5^6 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 7^6$	$95846 := -9^3 - 5^6 + 8^1 + 4^8 + 6^6$
$95286 := 9^5 + 5^5 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 6^3$	$95504 := 9^3 + 5^6 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 4^5$	$95847 := -9^2 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 - 7^4$
$95287 := 9^5 + 5^5 + 2^1 + 8^5 + 7^3$	$95567 := 9^1 + 5^4 + 5^7 + 6^0 + 7^5$	$95863 := -9^2 + 5^7 - 8^6 + 6^7 + 3^3$
$95327 := -9^2 + 5^7 + 3^9 + 2^0 - 7^4$	$95568 := 9^5 + 5^4 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 8^5$	$95874 := -9^2 + 5^7 - 8^0 + 7^5 + 4^5$
$95334 := -9^1 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 3^8 + 4^6$	$95572 := -9^4 + 5^3 - 5^6 + 7^6 - 2^4$	$95939 := -9^4 - 5^6 + 9^5 + 3^3 + 9^5$
$95337 := 9^2 + 5^7 + 3^4 + 3^5 + 7^5$	$95578 := 9^1 + 5^3 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^3$	$95974 := 9^1 + 5^7 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 4^5$
$95337 := -9^2 + 5^7 + 3^5 + 3^5 + 7^5$	$95579 := -9^1 + 5^3 - 5^6 + 7^6 - 9^4$	$95976 := -9^4 - 5^6 + 9^3 + 7^6 - 6^3$
$95342 := -9^4 + 5^7 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 2^0$	$95587 := -9^4 - 5^6 + 5^3 - 8^0 + 7^6$	$95993 := -9^4 - 5^6 + 9^5 + 9^5 + 3^4$
$95344 := 9^4 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 4^6$	$95596 := 9^1 + 5^5 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 6^5$	$96236 := 9^3 + 6^6 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 6^6$
$95344 := -9^4 + 5^7 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 4^6$	$95597 := -9^4 + 5^3 - 5^6 + 9^1 + 7^6$	$96275 := -9^2 + 6^4 + 2^7 + 7^5 + 5^7$
$95354 := -9^1 + 5^3 + 3^6 + 5^7 + 4^7$	$95627 := -9^3 + 5^7 + 6^4 + 2^7 + 7^5$	$96278 := -9^2 + 6^6 + 2^7 + 7^5 + 8^5$
$95357 := -9^2 - 5^2 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 7^6$	$95643 := -9^2 + 5^7 + 6^4 + 4^7 - 3^4$	$96365 := -9^2 + 6^6 + 3^2 + 6^6 + 5^5$
$95372 := -9^2 + 5^7 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 2^9$	$95678 := -9^4 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^6 - 8^0$	$96413 := 9^5 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 3^9$
$95373 := -9^1 - 5^6 - 3^4 + 7^6 - 3^8$	$95687 := -9^4 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1 + 7^6$	$96435 := -9^2 - 6^4 + 4^1 + 3^9 + 5^7$
$95374 := 9^5 + 5^5 + 3^2 + 7^5 + 4^7$	$95720 := -9^4 - 5^6 + 7^6 + 2^8 + 0^0$	$96453 := -9^2 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 3^6$
$95376 := -9^2 - 5^6 - 3^8 + 7^6 - 6^1$	$95726 := 9^3 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 2^6 + 6^0$	$96475 := -9^1 + 6^4 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 5^7$
$95379 := -9^2 - 5^6 - 3^1 + 7^6 - 9^4$	$95732 := -9^4 - 5^6 + 7^6 - 3^5 + 2^9$	$96478 := -9^1 + 6^6 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 8^5$
$95427 := -9^2 + 5^7 + 4^3 + 2^9 + 7^5$	$95733 := -9^1 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 3^4 + 3^6$	$96493 := 9^2 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 9^5 + 3^9$
$95437 := -9^4 - 5^6 + 4^0 - 3^3 + 7^6$	$95734 := 9^1 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 4^3$	$96495 := -9^2 + 6^6 + 4^8 + 9^1 - 5^6$
$95443 := -9^1 + 5^7 + 4^5 + 4^7 - 3^4$	$95737 := 9^3 + 5^7 + 7^2 + 3^3 + 7^5$	$96503 := -9^1 - 6^4 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 3^9$
$95446 := -9^2 + 5^7 + 4^5 + 4^7 - 6^1$	$95743 := 9^2 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 4^0 + 3^6$	$96526 := 9^2 + 6^6 + 5^5 + 2^3 + 6^6$
$95457 := -9^4 - 5^1 - 4^0 - 5^6 + 7^6$	$95774 := 9^3 + 5^7 + 7^2 + 7^5 + 4^3$	$96542 := -9^1 + 6^6 - 5^6 + 4^8 - 2^4$
$95462 := 9^3 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 2^3$	$95778 := -9^1 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 7^5 + 8^3$	$96542 := 9^3 + 6^4 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 2^3$
$95463 := 9^1 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 3^6$	$95779 := -9^1 + 5^5 + 7^5 + 7^5 + 9^5$	$96543 := 9^1 + 6^4 + 5^7 + 4^7 + 3^6$
		$96543 := -9^4 - 6^7 + 5^8 - 4^5 - 3^8$
		$96549 := -9^1 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 4^6 + 9^4$
		$96564 := -9^1 + 6^1 - 5^6 + 6^6 + 4^8$

$96564 := 9^4 + 6^1 + 5^7 + 6^5 + 4^6$	$97372 := -9^2 - 7^0 - 3^9 + 7^6 - 2^9$	$97935 := -9^3 + 7^5 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 5^5$
$96567 := 9^2 + 6^6 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 7^2$	$97385 := -9^2 - 7^3 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 5^7$	$97938 := -9^5 + 7^6 + 9^1 + 3^8 + 8^5$
$96583 := -9^4 - 6^5 + 5^7 + 8^5 + 3^3$	$97399 := -9^3 + 7^6 - 3^9 + 9^2 + 9^2$	$97953 := -9^1 + 7^6 - 9^1 + 5^1 - 3^9$
$96680 := -9^3 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 8^4 + 0^0$	$97443 := 9^4 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 3^8$	$97973 := -9^1 + 7^1 + 9^1 + 7^6 - 3^9$
$96735 := -9^3 - 6^0 - 7^3 + 3^9 + 5^7$	$97443 := -9^4 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 3^9$	$97978 := -9^5 + 7^2 + 9^4 + 7^6 + 8^5$
$96744 := 9^4 + 6^5 + 7^5 + 4^3 + 4^8$	$97466 := 9^1 + 7^2 + 4^6 + 6^6 + 6^6$	$98143 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 1^0 + 4^8 - 3^4$
$96745 := -9^6 - 6^5 - 7^5 + 4^9 + 5^8$	$97533 := -9^2 + 7^2 + 5^7 + 3^9 - 3^5$	$98224 := -9^2 + 8^5 - 2^0 + 2^1 + 4^8$
$96746 := 9^1 + 6^6 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 6^6$	$97537 := -9^2 - 7^3 - 5^1 - 3^9 + 7^6$	$98234 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^8$
$96765 := -9^4 + 6^1 + 7^6 + 6^4 - 5^6$	$97545 := -9^5 + 7^3 + 5^7 + 4^0 + 5^7$	$98235 := -9^2 + 8^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^7$
$96875 := -9^5 - 6^8 + 8^2 - 7^6 + 5^9$	$97552 := -9^5 + 7^3 + 5^7 + 5^7 + 2^3$	$98240 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 2^4 + 4^8 + 0^0$
$96879 := -9^2 + 6^6 + 8^5 + 7^5 + 9^3$	$97553 := -9^2 - 7^2 - 5^3 + 5^7 + 3^9$	$98247 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 2^0 + 4^8 - 7^2$
$96893 := -9^4 + 6^6 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 3^7$	$97554 := -9^2 + 7^0 + 5^5 + 5^7 + 4^7$	$98264 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 2^5 + 6^0 + 4^8$
$96963 := -9^4 + 6^1 + 9^5 + 6^6 - 3^7$	$97572 := -9^2 - 7^5 - 5^5 + 7^6 - 2^6$	$98274 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 7^2 + 4^8$
$96967 := -9^4 - 6^5 - 9^4 + 6^3 + 7^6$	$97645 := 9^3 + 7^4 + 6^1 + 4^7 + 5^7$	$98293 := -9^2 + 8^5 - 2^2 + 9^5 + 3^8$
$97223 := -9^3 + 7^6 - 2^4 + 2^1 - 3^9$	$97689 := 9^3 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 8^5 + 9^3$	$98294 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 2^1 + 9^0 + 4^8$
$97237 := -9^3 - 7^0 + 2^0 - 3^9 + 7^6$	$97733 := 9^5 + 7^1 + 7^5 + 3^7 + 3^9$	$98299 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 9^5$
$97243 := -9^3 + 7^6 + 2^1 + 4^1 - 3^9$	$97735 := -9^1 - 7^5 + 7^6 + 3^3 - 5^5$	$98304 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 4^8$
$97246 := -9^2 - 7^6 - 2^9 + 4^9 - 6^6$	$97753 := -9^2 - 7^1 + 7^6 - 5^3 - 3^9$	$98324 := 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 2^3 + 4^8$
$97248 := -9^3 - 7^3 + 2^4 + 4^8 + 8^5$	$97757 := -9^1 - 7^5 + 7^2 - 5^5 + 7^6$	$98324 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 3^1 + 2^5 + 4^8$
$97302 := -9^3 + 7^6 - 3^9 + 0^0 + 2^6$	$97757 := 9^2 + 7^3 + 7^4 + 5^7 + 7^5$	$98329 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 3^8 + 2^5 + 9^5$
$97319 := -9^3 + 7^6 - 3^9 + 1^0 + 9^2$	$97795 := -9^3 + 7^0 - 7^7 + 9^6 + 5^8$	$98340 := 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 0^1$
$97334 := -9^3 + 7^6 - 3^9 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$97823 := -9^2 + 7^6 - 8^2 + 2^1 - 3^9$	$98341 := 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 1^0$
$97335 := -9^1 + 7^6 - 3^9 + 3^1 - 5^4$	$97824 := -9^1 - 7^3 + 8^5 - 2^7 + 4^8$	$98342 := 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 2^1$
$97352 := -9^2 - 7^3 + 3^9 + 5^7 - 2^5$	$97826 := -9^1 - 7^6 + 8^6 - 2^2 - 6^6$	$98342 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 3^4 + 4^8 + 2^7$
$97353 := -9^1 + 7^5 + 3^5 + 5^7 + 3^7$	$97837 := -9^2 - 7^2 + 8^0 - 3^9 + 7^6$	$98343 := 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 4^8 + 3^3$
$97355 := -9^3 + 7^5 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 5^7$	$97846 := -9^1 - 7^6 + 8^6 + 4^2 - 6^6$	$98344 := 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 4^8$
$97356 := -9^3 + 7^6 - 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^1$	$97862 := -9^1 - 7^6 + 8^6 - 6^6 + 2^5$	$98345 := 9^1 + 8^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 5^7$
$97358 := -9^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 5^7 - 8^2$	$97866 := -9^1 - 7^6 + 8^6 + 6^2 - 6^6$	$98345 := -9^2 + 8^5 - 3^1 + 4^8 + 5^3$
$97359 := -9^5 + 7^6 + 3^9 + 5^7 - 9^5$	$97893 := -9^2 + 7^6 - 8^0 + 9^1 - 3^9$	$98346 := 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 6^1$
		$98347 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 4^8 + 7^2$
		$98347 := 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 7^1$
		$98348 := 9^1 + 8^1 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 8^5$

$98349 := 9^1 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 9^1$	$98539 := 9^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 3^9 + 9^0$	$98896 := 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 6^1$
$98349 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 3^3 + 4^8 + 9^2$	$98542 := 9^2 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 2^5$	$98897 := 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 7^1$
$98362 := -9^3 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 6^6 - 2^4$	$98543 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 3^5$	$98898 := 9^4 + 8^1 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 8^5$
$98365 := 9^1 + 8^3 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 5^7$	$98545 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 5^3$	$98899 := 9^1 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^4 + 9^5$
$98369 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 3^9 + 6^6 - 9^3$	$98546 := 9^2 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 6^2$	$98922 := 9^4 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 2^5 + 2^9$
$98380 := 9^5 + 8^0 + 3^8 + 8^5 + 0^0$	$98547 := -9^1 + 8^4 + 5^7 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$98926 := 9^4 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 2^9 + 6^2$
$98384 := -9^1 + 8^1 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 4^8$	$98564 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 6^3 + 4^8$	$98943 := -9^1 + 8^5 - 9^2 + 4^8 + 3^6$
$98386 := -9^3 + 8^1 + 3^9 + 8^5 + 6^6$	$98634 := 9^2 + 8^5 + 6^1 + 3^5 + 4^8$	$98946 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 + 4^8 - 6^1$
$98387 := 9^5 + 8^1 + 3^8 + 8^5 + 7^0$	$98634 := -9^3 + 8^5 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 4^4$	$99063 := -9^2 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^6 - 3^8$
$98388 := 9^2 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 8^5 + 8^5$	$98642 := 9^2 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 4^8 + 2^8$	$99146 := -9^4 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 6^6$
$98389 := 9^4 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 8^5 + 9^5$	$98654 := 9^1 + 8^5 + 6^3 + 5^3 + 4^8$	$99263 := -9^1 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 6^6 - 3^8$
$98402 := 9^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 0^0 + 2^4$	$98674 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 7^3 + 4^8$	$99265 := -9^4 + 9^5 - 2^2 + 6^6 + 5^3$
$98413 := 9^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 3^3$	$98693 := -9^3 - 8^4 + 6^6 + 9^5 - 3^7$	$99266 := -9^4 + 9^5 + 2^7 + 6^6 - 6^1$
$98422 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 2^7 - 2^0$	$98723 := 9^5 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 2^1 + 3^8$	$99396 := -9^4 + 9^1 + 3^5 + 9^5 + 6^6$
$98424 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 2^7 + 4^8$	$98729 := 9^4 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 2^3 + 9^5$	$99447 := -9^1 + 9^3 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 7^5$
$98432 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 2^7$	$98742 := -9^2 + 8^5 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 2^9$	$99464 := -9^4 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 6^6 + 4^4$
$98437 := 9^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 3^1 + 7^2$	$98744 := 9^1 + 8^1 + 7^5 + 4^7 + 4^8$	$99483 := 9^2 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 3^8$
$98442 := 9^1 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 4^8 + 2^7$	$98764 := 9^2 + 8^5 + 7^3 + 6^2 + 4^8$	$99643 := -9^4 + 9^5 + 6^6 + 4^4 + 3^5$
$98443 := 9^5 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 4^3 + 3^8$	$98784 := -9^2 + 8^3 + 7^2 + 8^5 + 4^8$	$99648 := -9^1 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 4^3 + 8^5$
$98452 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 5^3 + 2^5$	$98834 := 9^1 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 4^8$	$99662 := -9^4 + 9^5 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 2^9$
$98454 := 9^1 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 4^8$	$98834 := -9^1 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 3^3 + 4^8$	$99682 := 9^2 + 9^5 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 2^3$
$98456 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 5^3 + 6^2$	$98874 := 9^1 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 7^2 + 4^8$	$99683 := 9^1 + 9^5 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 3^8$
$98472 := -9^1 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 7^2 + 2^7$	$98890 := 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 0^1$	$99683 := -9^4 + 9^5 + 6^6 + 8^3 + 3^3$
$98473 := -9^1 + 8^3 + 4^1 + 7^6 - 3^9$	$98891 := 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 1^0$	$99758 := 9^3 + 9^0 + 7^5 + 5^7 + 8^4$
$98473 := 9^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 7^1 + 3^4$	$98892 := 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 2^1$	$99843 := 9^2 + 9^3 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 3^6$
$98493 := 9^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 9^2 + 3^3$	$98893 := 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 3^1$	$99843 := -9^3 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 3^7$
$98503 := 9^5 + 8^5 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 3^8$	$98894 := 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 4^1$	
$98536 := -9^4 - 8^0 + 5^7 - 3^9 + 6^6$	$98895 := 9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5 + 5^1$	

3 Fixed and Flexible Power Narcissistic Numbers with Division

Below are narcissistic numbers with division, having fixed and flexible powers in numerator and denominator and coefficients with positive and negative signs.

3.1 Single Digit Numbers

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 1 := \frac{1^0}{1^0} & 3 := \frac{3^1}{3^0} & 5 := \frac{5^1}{5^0} & 7 := \frac{7^1}{7^0} & 9 := \frac{9^1}{9^0} \\
 2 := \frac{2^1}{2^0} & 4 := \frac{4^1}{4^0} & 6 := \frac{6^1}{6^0} & 8 := \frac{8^1}{8^0} &
 \end{array}$$

3.2 Two Digits Numbers

$$\begin{array}{cccc}
 13 := \frac{-1^0 + 3^3}{1^0 + 3^0} & 26 := \frac{2^4 + 6^2}{2^0 + 6^0} & 42 := \frac{-4^1 + 2^8}{4^1 + 2^1} & 63 := \frac{6^3 - 3^3}{6^1 - 3^1} \\
 13 := \frac{-1^3 + 3^3}{1^0 + 3^0} & 26 := \frac{-2^3 + 6^3}{2^1 + 6^1} & 43 := \frac{4^2 + 3^3}{4^1 - 3^1} & 64 := \frac{6^4 - 4^2}{6^2 - 4^2} \\
 21 := \frac{2^6 - 1^0}{2^1 + 1^1} & 27 := \frac{2^5 + 7^2}{2^1 + 7^0} & 47 := \frac{-4^7 + 7^5}{4^2 - 7^1} & 68 := \frac{-6^2 + 8^3}{6^1 + 8^0} \\
 21 := \frac{2^6 - 1^6}{2^1 + 1^1} & 27 := \frac{2^5 + 7^2}{2^1 + 7^0} & 48 := \frac{4^3 + 8^3}{4^1 + 8^1} & 69 := \frac{6^3 - 9^1}{-6^1 + 9^1} \\
 22 := \frac{2^1 + 2^6}{2^0 + 2^1} & 28 := \frac{-2^3 + 8^2}{2^0 + 8^0} & 48 := \frac{4^3 + 8^3}{4^1 + 8^1} & 73 := \frac{7^2 + 3^5}{7^0 + 3^1} \\
 22 := \frac{2^1 + 2^6}{2^0 + 2^1} & 29 := \frac{2^6 + 9^2}{2^2 + 9^0} & 48 := \frac{4^3 + 8^3}{4^1 + 8^1} & 73 := \frac{7^2 + 3^5}{7^0 + 3^1} \\
 23 := \frac{-2^2 + 3^3}{2^1 - 3^0} & 29 := \frac{2^6 + 9^2}{2^2 + 9^0} & 53 := \frac{5^2 + 3^4}{5^0 + 3^0} & 75 := \frac{7^4 - 5^0}{7^1 + 5^2} \\
 24 := \frac{2^5 + 4^2}{2^0 + 4^0} & 37 := \frac{3^3 + 7^3}{3^1 + 7^1} & 53 := \frac{5^2 + 3^4}{5^0 + 3^0} & 84 := \frac{-8^2 + 4^6}{8^2 - 4^2} \\
 25 := \frac{2^{10} + 5^0}{2^4 + 5^2} & 37 := \frac{3^3 + 7^3}{3^1 + 7^1} & 57 := \frac{-5^0 + 7^3}{5^1 + 7^0} & 89 := \frac{8^1 + 9^2}{-8^1 + 9^1} \\
 25 := \frac{2^{10} + 5^0}{2^4 + 5^2} & 37 := \frac{3^3 + 7^3}{3^1 + 7^1} & 62 := \frac{6^3 + 2^5}{6^1 - 2^1} & 91 := \frac{9^3 - 1^0}{9^1 - 1^0} \\
 26 := \frac{2^4 + 6^2}{2^0 + 6^0} & 39 := \frac{-3^1 + 9^2}{3^0 + 9^0} & 63 := \frac{6^3 + 3^6}{6^1 + 3^2} & 91 := \frac{9^3 - 1^3}{9^1 - 1^1}
 \end{array}$$

3.3 Three Digits Numbers

$$102 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^9}{1^2 + 0^2 + 2^2}$$

$$123 := \frac{1^0 + 2^3 + 3^6}{1^1 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$123 := \frac{1^0 + 2^3 + 3^6}{1^1 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$125 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^0 + 5^3}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 5^0}$$

$$126 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^7 - 6^0}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$127 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^8 - 7^0}{-1^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$128 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^7 + 8^0}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$129 := \frac{1^0 + 2^8 + 9^0}{-1^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$132 := \frac{1^0 + 3^1 + 2^7}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$132 := \frac{-1^6 + 3^6 + 2^6}{1^1 + 3^1 + 2^1}$$

$$134 := \frac{-1^0 + 3^6 + 4^6}{-1^0 - 3^3 + 4^3}$$

$$134 := \frac{-1^6 + 3^6 + 4^6}{-1^3 - 3^3 + 4^3}$$

$$135 := \frac{1^0 + 3^2 + 5^3}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$136 := \frac{1^0 - 3^4 + 6^3}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$137 := \frac{1^0 + 3^9 - 7^5}{1^0 + 3^3 - 7^1}$$

$$138 := \frac{1^0 + 3^6 + 8^3}{-1^0 + 3^2 + 8^0}$$

$$139 := \frac{1^0 + 3^5 + 9^3}{-1^0 - 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$145 := \frac{1^0 + 4^3 + 5^5}{1^0 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$145 := \frac{1^0 + 4^3 + 5^5}{1^0 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$152 := \frac{1^0 + 5^7 + 2^1}{1^0 + 5^0 + 2^9}$$

$$152 := \frac{1^0 + 5^7 + 2^1}{1^0 + 5^0 + 2^9}$$

$$152 := \frac{-1^4 + 5^4 - 2^4}{1^1 + 5^1 - 2^1}$$

$$153 := \frac{1^3 + 5^3 + 3^3}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$153 := \frac{1^3 + 5^3 + 3^3}{1^0 + 5^0 - 3^0}$$

$$156 := \frac{1^0 + 5^5 - 6^1}{1^0 + 5^2 - 6^1}$$

$$158 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^4 + 8^1}{1^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$159 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^6 - 9^4}{1^0 - 5^2 + 9^2}$$

$$162 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^4 + 2^0}{1^0 + 6^1 + 2^0}$$

$$163 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^4 + 3^2}{1^0 + 6^1 + 3^0}$$

$$165 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^2 + 5^4}{-1^0 + 6^1 - 5^0}$$

$$169 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^5 - 9^0}{1^0 + 6^2 + 9^1}$$

$$172 := \frac{1^0 + 7^1 + 2^{10}}{1^0 + 7^0 + 2^2}$$

$$172 := \frac{1^0 + 7^1 + 2^{10}}{1^0 + 7^0 + 2^2}$$

$$174 := \frac{1^0 + 7^3 + 4^1}{-1^0 - 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$175 := \frac{1^0 + 7^2 + 5^3}{-1^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$183 := \frac{1^0 + 8^1 + 3^7}{1^1 + 8^1 + 3^1}$$

$$183 := \frac{1^0 + 8^1 + 3^7}{1^1 + 8^1 + 3^1}$$

$$192 := \frac{-1^0 + 9^4 - 2^5}{1^0 + 9^0 + 2^5}$$

$$195 := \frac{-1^0 + 9^4 - 5^3}{-1^0 + 9^1 + 5^2}$$

$$198 := \frac{1^0 + 9^2 + 8^3}{1^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$198 := \frac{1^0 + 9^2 + 8^3}{1^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$203 := \frac{2^3 + 0^1 + 3^9}{2^4 + 0^4 + 3^4}$$

$$203 := \frac{2^3 + 0^1 + 3^9}{2^4 + 0^4 + 3^4}$$

$$204 := \frac{-2^2 + 0^1 + 4^5}{2^0 + 0^1 + 4^1}$$

$$205 := \frac{2^{10} + 0^1 + 5^0}{2^2 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$205 := \frac{2^{10} + 0^1 + 5^0}{2^2 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$206 := \frac{2^{10} + 0^1 + 6^1}{2^2 + 0^1 + 6^0}$$

$$206 := \frac{2^{10} + 0^1 + 6^1}{2^2 + 0^1 + 6^0}$$

$$207 := \frac{2^8 + 0^1 - 7^2}{-2^0 + 0^0 + 7^0}$$

$$209 := \frac{2^7 + 0^1 + 9^2}{-2^0 + 0^0 + 9^0}$$

$$213 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 3^4}{2^3 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$213 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 3^4}{2^3 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$216 := \frac{-2^0 + 1^0 + 6^3}{-2^0 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$219 := \frac{2^{10} - 1^0 + 9^3}{-2^1 + 1^0 + 9^1}$$

$$221 := \frac{-2^4 + 2^{13} + 1^0}{2^2 + 2^5 + 1^0}$$

$$222 := \frac{-2^1 - 2^5 + 2^8}{-2^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$$

$$223 := \frac{2^6 + 2^{10} + 3^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 3^1}$$

$$223 := \frac{2^6 + 2^{10} + 3^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 3^1}$$

$$224 := \frac{2^7 + 2^9 + 4^4}{2^0 + 2^1 + 4^0}$$

$$224 := \frac{-2^4 - 2^4 + 4^4}{2^0 + 2^0 - 4^0}$$

$$225 := \frac{2^2 + 2^{12} + 5^4}{2^2 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$225 := \frac{2^2 + 2^{12} + 5^4}{2^2 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$226 := \frac{2^8 + 2^8 + 6^4}{2^0 + 2^0 + 6^1}$$

$$227 := \frac{2^5 + 2^6 + 7^4}{2^1 + 2^1 + 7^1}$$

$$227 := \frac{2^5 + 2^6 + 7^4}{2^1 + 2^1 + 7^1}$$

$$228 := \frac{2^2 + 2^2 + 8^4}{2^0 + 2^4 + 8^0}$$

$$228 := \frac{2^2 + 2^2 + 8^4}{2^0 + 2^4 + 8^0}$$

$$229 := \frac{2^2 + 2^{11} + 9^1}{2^2 + 2^2 + 9^0}$$

$$229 := \frac{2^2 + 2^{11} + 9^1}{2^2 + 2^2 + 9^0}$$

$$230 := \frac{2^8 - 3^3 + 0^0}{-2^0 + 3^0 + 0^0}$$

$$231 := \frac{2^{13} - 3^7 + 1^0}{2^4 + 3^2 + 1^0}$$

$$232 := \frac{-2^0 + 3^6 - 2^5}{2^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$233 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^6 + 3^9}{2^1 + 3^2 + 3^4}$$

$$233 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^6 + 3^9}{2^1 + 3^2 + 3^4}$$

$$234 := \frac{-2^3 + 3^5 - 4^0}{-2^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$235 := \frac{2^3 + 3^7 + 5^4}{2^1 + 3^2 + 5^0}$$

$$235 := \frac{2^3 + 3^7 + 5^4}{2^1 + 3^2 + 5^0}$$

$$236 := \frac{-2^0 + 3^5 - 6^1}{-2^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$237 := \frac{2^{13} + 3^7 + 7^2}{2^4 + 3^3 + 7^0}$$

$$237 := \frac{2^{13} + 3^7 + 7^2}{2^4 + 3^3 + 7^0}$$

$$238 := \frac{2^{19} + 3^{10} + 8^0}{2^8 + 3^7 + 8^1}$$

$$238 := \frac{2^{19} + 3^{10} + 8^0}{2^8 + 3^7 + 8^1}$$

$$239 := \frac{2^7 + 3^1 + 9^4}{2^4 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$239 := \frac{2^7 + 3^1 + 9^4}{2^4 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$240 := \frac{-2^4 + 4^4 + 0^1}{-2^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$240 := \frac{-2^4 + 4^4 - 0^4}{2^0 + 4^0 - 0^0}$$

$$241 := \frac{2^8 + 4^8 + 1^8}{2^4 + 4^4 + 1^4}$$

$$241 := \frac{2^8 + 4^8 + 1^8}{2^4 + 4^4 + 1^4}$$

$$241 := \frac{-2^4 + 4^4 + 1^4}{2^0 + 4^0 - 1^0}$$

$$242 := \frac{2^1 + 4^2 + 2^{12}}{2^3 + 4^0 + 2^3}$$

$$242 := \frac{2^1 + 4^2 + 2^{12}}{2^3 + 4^0 + 2^3}$$

$$243 := \frac{2^3 + 4^6 + 3^3}{2^2 + 4^1 + 3^2}$$

$$243 := \frac{2^3 + 4^6 + 3^3}{2^2 + 4^1 + 3^2}$$

$$244 := \frac{2^2 + 4^5 + 4^6}{2^0 + 4^1 + 4^2}$$

$$244 := \frac{2^2 + 4^5 + 4^6}{2^0 + 4^1 + 4^2}$$

$$245 := \frac{2^4 + 4^5 + 5^5}{2^3 + 4^1 + 5^1}$$

$$245 := \frac{2^4 + 4^5 + 5^5}{2^3 + 4^1 + 5^1}$$

$$246 := \frac{2^9 + 4^4 + 6^3}{2^1 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$246 := \frac{2^9 + 4^4 + 6^3}{2^1 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$247 := \frac{2^{15} + 4^7 + 7^0}{2^7 + 4^3 + 7^1}$$

$$247 := \frac{2^{15} + 4^7 + 7^0}{2^7 + 4^3 + 7^1}$$

$$248 := \frac{-2^3 - 4^4 + 8^3}{-2^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$249 := \frac{2^1 + 4^2 + 9^3}{2^0 + 4^0 + 9^0}$$

$$249 := \frac{2^1 + 4^2 + 9^3}{2^0 + 4^0 + 9^0}$$

$$250 := \frac{2^8 - 5^1 - 0^0}{-2^0 + 5^0 + 0^0}$$

$$251 := \frac{-2^6 + 5^6 + 1^0}{2^6 - 5^0 - 1^0}$$

$$252 := \frac{2^0 - 5^1 + 2^8}{-2^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$253 := \frac{2^4 + 5^0 + 3^8}{2^4 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$253 := \frac{2^4 + 5^0 + 3^8}{2^4 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$254 := \frac{2^7 + 5^3 + 4^0}{-2^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$255 := \frac{2^9 - 5^0 - 5^0}{2^1 - 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$256 := \frac{2^8 - 5^0 + 6^0}{-2^0 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$257 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^0 + 7^1}{2^1 + 5^1 + 7^0}$$

$$257 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^0 + 7^1}{2^1 + 5^1 + 7^0}$$

$$258 := \frac{2^8 + 5^0 + 8^0}{-2^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$259 := \frac{2^9 + 5^1 + 9^0}{2^1 - 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$260 := \frac{2^2 + 6^4 + 0^1}{2^2 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$260 := \frac{2^2 + 6^4 + 0^1}{2^2 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$261 := \frac{2^8 + 6^1 - 1^0}{-2^0 + 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$262 := \frac{2^9 + 6^2 + 2^{10}}{2^0 + 6^0 + 2^2}$$

$$263 := \frac{2^{10} + 6^0 + 3^3}{2^1 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$264 := \frac{2^9 + 6^3 + 4^3}{2^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$264 := \frac{2^4 + 6^4 - 4^4}{2^1 + 6^1 - 4^1}$$

$$265 := \frac{2^{10} + 6^5 + 5^5}{2^2 + 6^2 + 5^1}$$

$$265 := \frac{2^{10} + 6^5 + 5^5}{2^2 + 6^2 + 5^1}$$

$$266 := \frac{-2^{10} - 6^1 + 6^4}{-2^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$267 := \frac{2^0 + 6^0 + 7^4}{2^0 + 6^0 + 7^1}$$

$$268 := \frac{2^8 + 6^2 + 8^3}{2^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$268 := \frac{2^8 + 6^2 + 8^3}{2^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$269 := \frac{2^{10} - 6^3 - 9^0}{2^0 + 6^0 + 9^0}$$

$$270 := \frac{-2^9 + 7^4 + 0^0}{-2^0 + 7^1 + 0^0}$$

$$271 := \frac{-2^2 + 7^5 - 1^0}{2^6 - 7^0 - 1^0}$$

$$272 := \frac{-2^0 + 7^6 - 2^{11}}{2^1 + 7^5 - 2^{14}}$$

$$273 := \frac{2^9 + 7^1 + 3^9}{2^4 + 7^2 + 3^2}$$

$$273 := \frac{2^9 + 7^1 + 3^9}{2^4 + 7^2 + 3^2}$$

$$274 := \frac{2^0 + 7^4 + 4^3}{2^0 + 7^1 + 4^0}$$

$$274 := \frac{2^0 + 7^4 + 4^3}{2^0 + 7^1 + 4^0}$$

$$275 := \frac{2^{10} + 7^0 + 5^4}{2^2 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$275 := \frac{2^{10} + 7^0 + 5^4}{2^2 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$276 := \frac{-2^0 + 7^4 - 6^4}{2^1 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$277 := \frac{2^{14} + 7^2 + 7^5}{2^6 + 7^1 + 7^2}$$

$$277 := \frac{2^{14} + 7^2 + 7^5}{2^6 + 7^1 + 7^2}$$

$$278 := \frac{-2^0 + 7^3 - 8^2}{-2^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$279 := \frac{2^7 + 7^1 + 9^4}{2^3 + 7^1 + 9^1}$$

$$279 := \frac{2^7 + 7^1 + 9^4}{2^3 + 7^1 + 9^1}$$

$$282 := \frac{2^3 - 8^2 + 2^{15}}{-2^2 - 8^1 + 2^7}$$

$$283 := \frac{2^8 + 8^3 + 3^4}{2^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$284 := \frac{-2^3 + 8^3 + 4^3}{-2^0 - 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$284 := \frac{-2^3 + 8^3 + 4^3}{-2^1 + 8^1 - 4^1}$$

$$285 := \frac{2^1 + 8^1 + 5^5}{2^1 + 8^1 + 5^0}$$

$$285 := \frac{2^1 + 8^1 + 5^5}{2^1 + 8^1 + 5^0}$$

$$286 := \frac{2^{17} + 8^5 + 6^6}{2^3 + 8^3 + 6^3}$$

$$286 := \frac{2^{17} + 8^5 + 6^6}{2^3 + 8^3 + 6^3}$$

$$287 := \frac{2^3 - 8^2 + 7^3}{-2^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$288 := \frac{2^7 + 8^3 + 8^3}{2^1 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$288 := \frac{2^7 + 8^3 + 8^3}{2^1 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$289 := \frac{2^{14} + 8^1 + 9^2}{2^1 + 8^2 - 9^1}$$

$$290 := \frac{2^{15} + 9^0 + 0^0}{2^5 + 9^2 + 0^1}$$

$$290 := \frac{2^{15} + 9^0 + 0^0}{2^5 + 9^2 + 0^1}$$

$$292 := \frac{-2^0 + 9^3 + 2^{10}}{2^0 + 9^0 + 2^2}$$

$$293 := \frac{2^{13} + 9^1 + 3^1}{2^4 + 9^1 + 3^1}$$

$$293 := \frac{2^{13} + 9^1 + 3^1}{2^4 + 9^1 + 3^1}$$

$$294 := \frac{2^{11} + 9^1 + 4^0}{2^1 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$294 := \frac{2^{11} + 9^1 + 4^0}{2^1 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$295 := \frac{2^{12} + 9^1 + 5^2}{2^2 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$295 := \frac{2^{12} + 9^1 + 5^2}{2^2 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$296 := \frac{-2^0 + 9^2 + 6^3}{-2^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$297 := \frac{2^{17} + 9^4 + 7^5}{2^9 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$297 := \frac{2^{17} + 9^4 + 7^5}{2^9 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$298 := \frac{2^{14} + 9^4 + 8^0}{2^2 + 9^1 + 8^2}$$

$$298 := \frac{2^{14} + 9^4 + 8^0}{2^2 + 9^1 + 8^2}$$

$$299 := \frac{2^{12} + 9^1 + 9^2}{2^2 + 9^0 + 9^1}$$

$$299 := \frac{2^{12} + 9^1 + 9^2}{2^2 + 9^0 + 9^1}$$

$$302 := \frac{-3^0 - 0^0 + 2^{16}}{3^6 + 0^1 - 2^9}$$

$$308 := \frac{3^5 + 0^0 + 8^2}{-3^0 + 0^0 + 8^0}$$

$$312 := \frac{3^7 - 1^0 - 2^1}{3^2 - 1^0 - 2^0}$$

$$313 := \frac{3^1 + 1^0 + 3^7}{3^1 + 1^1 + 3^1}$$

$$313 := \frac{3^1 + 1^0 + 3^7}{3^1 + 1^1 + 3^1}$$

$$314 := \frac{-3^4 - 1^0 + 4^5}{3^0 + 1^0 + 4^0}$$

$$317 := \frac{-3^3 + 1^0 + 7^3}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 7^0}$$

$$317 := \frac{-3^3 + 1^3 + 7^3}{3^0 + 1^0 - 7^0}$$

$$318 := \frac{-3^7 - 1^0 + 8^4}{-3^0 - 1^0 + 8^1}$$

$$321 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{10} - 1^0}{3^0 + 2^3 + 1^0}$$

$$322 := \frac{3^7 + 2^0 - 2^8}{3^0 + 2^0 + 2^2}$$

$$323 := \frac{3^4 - 2^0 + 3^5}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$324 := \frac{-3^3 - 2^0 + 4^9}{3^6 + 2^4 + 4^3}$$

$$325 := \frac{3^3 + 2^{11} + 5^5}{3^1 + 2^3 + 5^1}$$

$$325 := \frac{3^3 + 2^{11} + 5^5}{3^1 + 2^3 + 5^1}$$

$$326 := \frac{3^2 - 2^0 + 6^4}{3^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$327 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{11} + 7^3}{3^1 + 2^2 + 7^1}$$

$$327 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{11} + 7^3}{3^1 + 2^2 + 7^1}$$

$$328 := \frac{3^6 + 2^8 - 8^0}{3^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$329 := \frac{3^1 + 2^4 + 9^4}{3^1 + 2^3 + 9^1}$$

$$329 := \frac{3^1 + 2^4 + 9^4}{3^1 + 2^3 + 9^1}$$

$$332 := \frac{3^2 + 3^7 + 2^7}{3^1 + 3^1 + 2^0}$$

$$333 := \frac{3^3 + 3^5 + 3^6}{3^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$334 := \frac{3^1 + 3^5 + 4^6}{3^1 + 3^2 + 4^0}$$

$$335 := \frac{3^4 + 3^9 + 5^0}{3^3 + 3^3 + 5^1}$$

$$335 := \frac{3^4 + 3^9 + 5^0}{3^3 + 3^3 + 5^1}$$

$$336 := \frac{3^5 + 3^6 + 6^2}{3^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$336 := \frac{3^5 + 3^6 + 6^2}{3^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$337 := \frac{3^7 + 3^7 + 7^1}{3^1 + 3^1 + 7^1}$$

$$337 := \frac{3^7 + 3^7 + 7^1}{3^1 + 3^1 + 7^1}$$

$$338 := \frac{3^7 + 3^8 + 8^4}{3^1 + 3^3 + 8^1}$$

$$338 := \frac{3^7 + 3^8 + 8^4}{3^1 + 3^3 + 8^1}$$

$$340 := \frac{-3^1 + 4^5 - 0^0}{3^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$341 := \frac{-3^1 + 4^6 - 1^0}{-3^1 + 4^2 - 1^0}$$

$$342 := \frac{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^{10}}{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$342 := \frac{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^{10}}{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$343 := \frac{3^6 + 4^4 + 3^8}{3^1 + 4^2 + 3^1}$$

$$343 := \frac{3^6 + 4^4 + 3^8}{3^1 + 4^2 + 3^1}$$

$$344 := \frac{3^2 - 4^0 + 4^5}{3^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$345 := \frac{3^6 + 4^6 + 5^1}{3^2 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$345 := \frac{3^6 + 4^6 + 5^1}{3^2 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$346 := \frac{3^6 - 4^0 - 6^2}{-3^0 + 4^1 - 6^0}$$

$$347 := \frac{3^1 + 4^0 + 7^3}{-3^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$348 := \frac{3^4 - 4^0 + 8^4}{3^1 + 4^0 + 8^1}$$

$$349 := \frac{3^7 + 4^5 + 9^4}{3^1 + 4^2 + 9^1}$$

$$349 := \frac{3^7 + 4^5 + 9^4}{3^1 + 4^2 + 9^1}$$

$$352 := \frac{3^3 + 5^1 + 2^{10}}{3^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$352 := \frac{3^3 + 5^1 + 2^{10}}{3^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$353 := \frac{-3^5 - 5^2 + 3^9}{3^1 + 5^2 + 3^3}$$

$$354 := \frac{3^3 + 5^3 + 4^6}{3^1 + 5^1 + 4^1}$$

$$354 := \frac{3^3 + 5^3 + 4^6}{3^1 + 5^1 + 4^1}$$

$$355 := \frac{3^{11} - 5^0 - 5^0}{-3^0 - 5^3 + 5^4}$$

$$356 := \frac{3^7 + 5^4 + 6^2}{3^0 + 5^0 + 6^1}$$

$$356 := \frac{3^7 + 5^4 + 6^2}{3^0 + 5^0 + 6^1}$$

$$357 := \frac{3^4 + 5^5 + 7^1}{3^0 + 5^0 + 7^1}$$

$$358 := \frac{3^3 + 5^4 + 8^2}{-3^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$359 := \frac{3^5 + 5^3 - 9^1}{-3^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$361 := \frac{3^6 - 6^1 - 1^0}{-3^1 + 6^1 - 1^0}$$

$$362 := \frac{3^6 - 6^0 - 2^2}{-3^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$363 := \frac{3^1 - 6^1 + 3^6}{-3^0 + 6^1 - 3^1}$$

$$364 := \frac{3^7 + 6^0 - 4^1}{3^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$365 := \frac{3^6 + 6^1 - 5^1}{3^0 + 6^1 - 5^1}$$

$$367 := \frac{3^8 + 6^5 + 7^3}{3^1 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$367 := \frac{3^8 + 6^5 + 7^3}{3^1 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$368 := \frac{3^6 + 6^1 + 8^0}{-3^1 + 6^1 - 8^0}$$

$$369 := \frac{3^7 + 6^2 + 9^3}{3^0 + 6^1 + 9^0}$$

$$369 := \frac{3^7 + 6^2 + 9^3}{3^0 + 6^1 + 9^0}$$

$$370 := \frac{3^3 + 7^3 + 0^3}{-3^0 + 7^0 + 0^0}$$

$$370 := \frac{3^3 + 7^3 - 0^3}{3^0 + 7^0 - 0^0}$$

$$371 := \frac{3^3 + 7^3 + 1^3}{-3^0 + 7^0 + 1^0}$$

$$371 := \frac{3^3 + 7^3 + 1^3}{3^0 + 7^0 - 1^0}$$

$$372 := \frac{3^8 + 7^1 + 2^7}{3^0 + 7^0 + 2^4}$$

$$373 := \frac{3^4 + 7^3 + 3^7}{3^1 + 7^0 + 3^1}$$

$$374 := \frac{3^3 + 7^3 + 4^1}{-3^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$375 := \frac{3^5 + 7^1 + 5^5}{3^0 + 7^1 + 5^0}$$

$$376 := \frac{3^{10} + 7^7 + 6^5}{3^6 + 7^3 + 6^4}$$

$$377 := \frac{3^3 + 7^1 + 7^3}{-3^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$378 := \frac{3^9 + 7^3 + 8^1}{3^1 + 7^2 + 8^0}$$

$$379 := \frac{3^3 + 7^3 + 9^1}{-3^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$382 := \frac{3^5 + 8^0 + 2^{11}}{3^0 + 8^0 + 2^2}$$

$$382 := \frac{3^5 + 8^0 + 2^{11}}{3^0 + 8^0 + 2^2}$$

$$383 := \frac{-3^3 + 8^2 + 3^6}{3^0 - 8^1 + 3^2}$$

$$385 := \frac{3^8 + 8^6 + 5^2}{3^2 + 8^2 + 5^4}$$

$$385 := \frac{3^8 + 8^6 + 5^2}{3^2 + 8^2 + 5^4}$$

$$386 := \frac{-3^6 + 8^5 - 6^0}{3^4 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$387 := \frac{3^6 + 8^0 - 7^3}{-3^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$392 := \frac{-3^4 + 9^3 - 2^8}{-3^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$394 := \frac{3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5}{-3^1 + 9^1 + 4^1}$$

$$396 := \frac{3^5 + 9^3 + 6^3}{3^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$396 := \frac{3^5 + 9^3 + 6^3}{3^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$397 := \frac{-3^3 + 9^2 + 7^3}{-3^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$398 := \frac{3^1 + 9^3 + 8^2}{3^0 + 9^1 - 8^1}$$

$$405 := \frac{4^7 + 0^0 + 5^4}{4^2 + 0^0 + 5^2}$$

$$405 := \frac{4^7 + 0^0 + 5^4}{4^2 + 0^0 + 5^2}$$

$$406 := \frac{4^6 + 0^1 - 6^2}{4^1 + 0^1 + 6^1}$$

$$407 := \frac{4^3 + 0^3 + 7^3}{-4^0 + 0^0 + 7^0}$$

$$407 := \frac{4^3 - 0^3 + 7^3}{4^0 + 0^0 - 7^0}$$

$$408 := \frac{-4^2 + 0^1 + 8^4}{4^0 + 0^0 + 8^1}$$

$$409 := \frac{4^4 + 0^1 + 9^5}{4^3 + 0^1 + 9^2}$$

$$409 := \frac{4^4 + 0^1 + 9^5}{4^3 + 0^1 + 9^2}$$

$$415 := \frac{4^5 + 1^5 + 5^5}{4^1 + 1^1 + 5^1}$$

$$415 := \frac{4^5 + 1^5 + 5^5}{4^1 + 1^1 + 5^1}$$

$$415 := \frac{4^5 + 1^5 + 5^5}{4^1 + 1^1 + 5^1}$$

$$422 := \frac{4^3 - 2^1 + 2^{11}}{4^0 + 2^1 + 2^1}$$

$$423 := \frac{4^5 + 2^1 + 3^5}{4^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$423 := \frac{4^5 + 2^1 + 3^5}{4^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$424 := \frac{4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6}{4^1 + 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$424 := \frac{4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6}{4^1 + 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$425 := \frac{4^1 + 2^{12} + 5^5}{4^1 + 2^3 + 5^1}$$

$$425 := \frac{4^1 + 2^{12} + 5^5}{4^1 + 2^3 + 5^1}$$

$$426 := \frac{4^3 + 2^{11} + 6^4}{4^0 + 2^0 + 6^1}$$

$$426 := \frac{4^3 + 2^{11} + 6^4}{4^0 + 2^0 + 6^1}$$

$$427 := \frac{4^4 + 2^{10} + 7^0}{4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$427 := \frac{4^4 + 2^{10} + 7^0}{4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$428 := \frac{4^2 + 2^{10} + 8^4}{-4^1 + 2^3 + 8^1}$$

$$429 := \frac{4^4 + 2^{15} + 9^1}{4^1 + 2^6 + 9^1}$$

$$429 := \frac{4^4 + 2^{15} + 9^1}{4^1 + 2^6 + 9^1}$$

$$432 := \frac{4^0 - 3^4 + 2^9}{-4^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$433 := \frac{4^4 + 3^3 + 3^{12}}{4^4 + 3^5 + 3^6}$$

$$433 := \frac{4^4 + 3^3 + 3^{12}}{4^4 + 3^5 + 3^6}$$

$$434 := \frac{-4^0 + 3^7 - 4^2}{4^0 + 3^1 + 4^0}$$

$$435 := \frac{4^{12} + 3^6 + 5^1}{4^7 + 3^8 + 5^6}$$

$$435 := \frac{4^{12} + 3^6 + 5^1}{4^7 + 3^8 + 5^6}$$

$$436 := \frac{-4^0 + 3^7 - 6^1}{4^0 + 3^1 + 6^0}$$

$$437 := \frac{-4^0 + 3^7 - 7^0}{4^0 + 3^1 + 7^0}$$

$$438 := \frac{4^0 + 3^8 + 8^1}{4^1 + 3^1 + 8^1}$$

$$438 := \frac{4^0 + 3^8 + 8^1}{4^1 + 3^1 + 8^1}$$

$$439 := \frac{4^5 + 3^1 + 9^3}{4^1 - 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$443 := \frac{-4^1 + 4^4 + 3^9}{-4^2 + 4^3 - 3^1}$$

$$445 := \frac{4^3 + 4^4 + 5^3}{-4^0 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$446 := \frac{-4^1 + 4^4 + 6^5}{4^0 + 4^2 + 6^0}$$

$$448 := \frac{4^4 + 4^5 + 8^2}{4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$448 := \frac{4^4 + 4^5 + 8^2}{4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$448 := \frac{-4^4 - 4^4 + 8^4}{4^1 - 4^1 + 8^1}$$

$$449 := \frac{-4^3 + 4^6 + 9^1}{4^1 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$450 := \frac{4^5 - 5^3 + 0^0}{4^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$452 := \frac{-4^0 + 5^6 - 2^8}{4^0 + 5^0 + 2^5}$$

$$453 := \frac{4^4 + 5^5 + 3^5}{4^1 + 5^0 + 3^1}$$

$$453 := \frac{4^4 + 5^5 + 3^5}{4^1 + 5^0 + 3^1}$$

$$455 := \frac{4^7 + 5^0 - 5^1}{4^2 - 5^1 + 5^2}$$

$$456 := \frac{4^0 - 5^2 + 6^5}{4^2 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$457 := \frac{4^4 + 5^0 + 7^6}{4^4 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$457 := \frac{4^4 + 5^0 + 7^6}{4^4 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$458 := \frac{4^0 + 5^2 + 8^4}{-4^1 + 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$459 := \frac{4^7 + 5^1 + 9^4}{4^2 + 5^2 + 9^1}$$

$$459 := \frac{4^7 + 5^1 + 9^4}{4^2 + 5^2 + 9^1}$$

$$460 := \frac{-4^6 + 6^5 + 0^1}{4^0 + 6^1 + 0^0}$$

$$462 := \frac{4^7 + 6^4 + 2^{13}}{4^2 + 6^2 + 2^2}$$

$$462 := \frac{4^7 + 6^4 + 2^{13}}{4^2 + 6^2 + 2^2}$$

$$463 := \frac{4^2 + 6^5 + 3^8}{4^2 + 6^1 + 3^2}$$

$$464 := \frac{-4^2 - 6^4 + 4^6}{4^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$465 := \frac{4^5 + 6^4 + 5^1}{-4^0 + 6^0 + 5^1}$$

$$466 := \frac{4^4 - 6^1 + 6^3}{-4^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$467 := \frac{4^1 + 6^0 + 7^5}{-4^0 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$468 := \frac{4^9 + 6^4 + 8^3}{4^2 + 6^2 + 8^3}$$

$$468 := \frac{4^9 + 6^4 + 8^3}{4^2 + 6^2 + 8^3}$$

$$469 := \frac{4^1 + 6^0 + 9^4}{4^1 + 6^0 + 9^1}$$

$$469 := \frac{4^1 + 6^0 + 9^4}{4^1 + 6^0 + 9^1}$$

$$472 := \frac{4^0 + 7^3 + 2^7}{-4^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$473 := \frac{4^7 - 7^1 - 3^7}{4^1 - 7^0 + 3^3}$$

$$475 := \frac{4^0 + 7^2 + 5^6}{4^0 + 7^1 + 5^2}$$

$$475 := \frac{4^0 + 7^2 + 5^6}{4^0 + 7^1 + 5^2}$$

$$476 := \frac{-4^0 - 7^3 + 6^4}{4^0 + 7^1 - 6^1}$$

$$479 := \frac{-4^4 + 7^4 + 9^3}{4^1 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$480 := \frac{4^5 - 8^2 + 0^1}{4^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$482 := \frac{4^0 + 8^0 + 2^{13}}{4^0 + 8^1 + 2^3}$$

$$482 := \frac{4^0 + 8^0 + 2^{13}}{4^0 + 8^1 + 2^3}$$

$$483 := \frac{-4^4 + 8^0 + 3^7}{-4^0 + 8^1 - 3^1}$$

$$484 := \frac{4^1 + 8^4 + 4^4}{4^1 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$484 := \frac{4^1 + 8^4 + 4^4}{4^1 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$485 := \frac{4^5 + 8^4 + 5^5}{4^1 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$485 := \frac{4^5 + 8^4 + 5^5}{4^1 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$486 := \frac{4^6 + 8^1 - 6^3}{4^0 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$487 := \frac{-4^7 + 8^2 + 7^5}{-4^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$488 := \frac{-4^2 - 8^1 + 8^3}{-4^0 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$489 := \frac{-4^1 + 8^5 - 9^0}{4^1 + 8^2 - 9^0}$$

$$492 := \frac{-4^0 + 9^3 + 2^8}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$493 := \frac{4^4 + 9^0 + 3^6}{4^1 - 9^0 - 3^0}$$

$$494 := \frac{-4^0 - 9^2 + 4^7}{4^2 + 9^0 + 4^2}$$

$$495 := \frac{4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3}{4^1 + 9^0 + 5^1}$$

$$495 := \frac{4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3}{4^1 + 9^0 + 5^1}$$

$$497 := \frac{-4^2 + 9^4 + 7^4}{4^2 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$499 := \frac{4^7 + 9^1 + 9^4}{4^3 - 9^1 - 9^1}$$

$$502 := \frac{5^6 + 0^0 - 2^6}{-5^0 + 0^1 + 2^5}$$

$$508 := \frac{-5^1 + 0^0 + 8^3}{-5^0 + 0^0 + 8^0}$$

$$509 := \frac{-5^1 + 0^1 + 9^5}{5^3 + 0^1 - 9^1}$$

$$512 := \frac{-5^0 + 1^0 + 2^9}{-5^0 + 1^0 + 2^0}$$

$$514 := \frac{5^1 - 1^0 + 4^5}{-5^0 - 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$518 := \frac{5^1 + 1^0 + 8^3}{-5^0 + 1^0 + 8^0}$$

$$520 := \frac{5^5 - 2^2 - 0^0}{5^0 + 2^2 + 0^0}$$

$$521 := \frac{5^6 + 2^2 + 1^0}{5^2 + 2^2 + 1^2}$$

$$521 := \frac{5^6 + 2^2 + 1^0}{5^2 + 2^2 + 1^2}$$

$$522 := \frac{5^5 - 2^0 + 2^3}{5^0 + 2^0 + 2^2}$$

$$523 := \frac{5^5 + 2^2 + 3^2}{5^0 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$523 := \frac{5^5 + 2^2 + 3^2}{5^0 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$524 := \frac{5^2 - 2^0 + 4^5}{-5^0 - 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$525 := \frac{5^0 + 2^{10} + 5^2}{-5^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$526 := \frac{5^5 + 2^5 - 6^0}{5^0 + 2^2 + 6^0}$$

$$527 := \frac{-5^6 - 2^7 + 7^5}{-5^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$529 := \frac{5^6 + 2^5 + 9^4}{5^0 + 2^5 + 9^1}$$

$$529 := \frac{5^6 + 2^5 + 9^4}{5^0 + 2^5 + 9^1}$$

$$532 := \frac{5^5 + 3^1 + 2^6}{5^0 + 3^0 + 2^2}$$

$$532 := \frac{5^5 + 3^1 + 2^6}{5^0 + 3^0 + 2^2}$$

$$533 := \frac{5^3 + 3^5 + 3^8}{5^0 + 3^1 + 3^2}$$

$$533 := \frac{5^3 + 3^5 + 3^8}{5^0 + 3^1 + 3^2}$$

$$534 := \frac{5^3 + 3^7 + 4^6}{5^1 + 3^1 + 4^1}$$

$$534 := \frac{5^3 + 3^7 + 4^6}{5^1 + 3^1 + 4^1}$$

$$536 := \frac{-5^2 + 3^0 + 6^6}{5^1 + 3^4 + 6^0}$$

$$537 := \frac{5^4 - 3^4 - 7^1}{-5^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$538 := \frac{5^6 + 3^3 + 8^5}{5^0 + 3^4 + 8^1}$$

$$539 := \frac{5^5 - 3^4 + 9^3}{5^1 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$542 := \frac{5^5 - 4^0 + 2^7}{5^0 + 4^0 + 2^2}$$

$$543 := \frac{5^1 + 4^6 + 3^5}{5^0 + 4^1 + 3^1}$$

$$543 := \frac{5^1 + 4^6 + 3^5}{5^0 + 4^1 + 3^1}$$

$$546 := \frac{-5^1 + 4^7 + 6^0}{5^2 + 4^1 + 6^0}$$

$$547 := \frac{5^4 + 4^4 + 7^4}{5^0 + 4^1 + 7^0}$$

$$547 := \frac{5^4 + 4^4 + 7^4}{5^0 + 4^1 + 7^0}$$

$$547 := \frac{5^4 + 4^4 + 7^4}{-5^1 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$549 := \frac{5^1 + 4^7 + 9^2}{5^1 + 4^2 + 9^1}$$

$$549 := \frac{5^1 + 4^7 + 9^2}{5^1 + 4^2 + 9^1}$$

$$553 := \frac{-5^3 + 5^7 - 3^3}{5^2 + 5^3 - 3^2}$$

$$554 := \frac{-5^6 + 5^7 + 4^9}{5^2 + 5^4 - 4^3}$$

$$556 := \frac{-5^1 + 5^5 + 6^3}{-5^0 + 5^0 + 6^1}$$

$$557 := \frac{-5^4 - 5^6 + 7^5}{-5^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$559 := \frac{-5^3 + 5^5 + 9^5}{5^1 + 5^2 + 9^2}$$

$$562 := \frac{5^4 + 6^0 - 2^6}{-5^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$563 := \frac{5^2 + 6^4 + 3^8}{5^1 + 6^1 + 3^1}$$

$$563 := \frac{5^2 + 6^4 + 3^8}{5^1 + 6^1 + 3^1}$$

$$564 := \frac{5^6 + 6^4 - 4^0}{5^2 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$565 := \frac{5^0 - 6^7 + 5^{11}}{5^2 + 6^5 + 5^7}$$

$$567 := \frac{5^3 + 6^4 + 7^6}{5^3 + 6^2 + 7^2}$$

$$567 := \frac{5^3 + 6^4 + 7^6}{5^3 + 6^2 + 7^2}$$

$$568 := \frac{5^4 - 6^0 + 8^3}{-5^1 - 6^0 + 8^1}$$

$$569 := \frac{5^4 - 6^3 + 9^3}{-5^0 - 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$572 := \frac{5^4 - 7^2 - 2^2}{-5^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$573 := \frac{5^3 + 7^5 + 3^8}{5^2 + 7^1 + 3^2}$$

$$573 := \frac{5^3 + 7^5 + 3^8}{5^2 + 7^1 + 3^2}$$

$$574 := \frac{-5^2 + 7^3 + 4^4}{-5^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$575 := \frac{-5^0 - 7^2 + 5^4}{-5^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$576 := \frac{-5^4 + 7^2 + 6^6}{5^2 + 7^2 + 6^1}$$

$$577 := \frac{5^4 + 7^0 - 7^2}{-5^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$578 := \frac{-5^2 + 7^4 - 8^2}{-5^1 + 7^0 + 8^1}$$

$$579 := \frac{5^6 + 7^1 + 9^0}{5^2 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$579 := \frac{5^6 + 7^1 + 9^0}{5^2 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$580 := \frac{5^6 + 8^4 - 0^0}{5^2 + 8^1 + 0^0}$$

$$582 := \frac{-5^4 - 8^0 + 2^{13}}{5^0 + 8^1 + 2^2}$$

$$583 := \frac{5^5 + 8^3 + 3^9}{5^1 + 8^1 + 3^3}$$

$$583 := \frac{5^5 + 8^3 + 3^9}{5^1 + 8^1 + 3^3}$$

$$584 := \frac{5^6 - 8^0 - 4^5}{5^0 + 8^1 + 4^2}$$

$$586 := \frac{5^1 + 8^4 + 6^0}{5^1 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$586 := \frac{5^1 + 8^4 + 6^0}{5^1 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$587 := \frac{-5^6 - 8^1 + 7^5}{5^0 + 8^1 - 7^1}$$

$$589 := \frac{5^4 + 8^4 - 9^1}{-5^0 + 8^1 + 9^0}$$

$$592 := \frac{-5^0 + 9^2 + 2^9}{-5^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$593 := \frac{-5^7 + 9^1 + 3^{11}}{5^1 + 9^2 + 3^4}$$

$$594 := \frac{5^5 + 9^1 + 4^5}{5^1 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$594 := \frac{5^5 + 9^1 + 4^5}{5^1 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$596 := \frac{5^4 - 9^3 + 6^4}{-5^0 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$597 := \frac{5^1 + 9^4 + 7^0}{5^0 + 9^1 + 7^0}$$

$$597 := \frac{5^1 + 9^4 + 7^0}{5^0 + 9^1 + 7^0}$$

$$598 := \frac{5^6 + 9^1 + 8^3}{5^2 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$603 := \frac{6^3 + 0^1 + 3^9}{6^1 + 0^1 + 3^3}$$

$$603 := \frac{6^3 + 0^1 + 3^9}{6^1 + 0^1 + 3^3}$$

$$604 := \frac{6^5 + 0^1 + 4^7}{6^2 + 0^1 + 4^1}$$

$$604 := \frac{6^5 + 0^1 + 4^7}{6^2 + 0^1 + 4^1}$$

$$608 := \frac{6^6 + 0^1 - 8^4}{6^1 + 0^1 + 8^2}$$

$$613 := \frac{6^6 - 1^0 - 3^9}{6^2 - 1^0 + 3^2}$$

$$620 := \frac{6^3 + 2^{10} + 0^1}{6^0 + 2^0 + 0^1}$$

$$620 := \frac{6^3 + 2^{10} + 0^1}{6^0 + 2^0 + 0^1}$$

$$622 := \frac{6^5 + 2^7 + 2^{11}}{6^1 + 2^1 + 2^3}$$

$$622 := \frac{6^5 + 2^7 + 2^{11}}{6^1 + 2^1 + 2^3}$$

$$623 := \frac{6^2 + 2^8 + 3^8}{6^1 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$623 := \frac{6^2 + 2^8 + 3^8}{6^1 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$624 := \frac{6^4 + 2^9 + 4^3}{6^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$624 := \frac{6^4 + 2^9 + 4^3}{6^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$625 := \frac{6^7 + 2^6 + 5^6}{6^3 + 2^8 + 5^0}$$

$$625 := \frac{6^7 + 2^6 + 5^6}{6^3 + 2^8 + 5^0}$$

$$626 := \frac{-6^2 - 2^3 + 6^4}{-6^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$627 := \frac{-6^3 + 2^{11} + 7^2}{6^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$628 := \frac{6^5 + 2^7 + 8^7}{6^4 + 2^{11} + 8^1}$$

$$628 := \frac{6^5 + 2^7 + 8^7}{6^4 + 2^{11} + 8^1}$$

$$629 := \frac{6^2 + 2^{12} + 9^4}{6^1 + 2^1 + 9^1}$$

$$632 := \frac{-6^0 + 3^8 + 2^{10}}{6^0 + 3^1 + 2^3}$$

$$633 := \frac{6^4 - 3^1 - 3^3}{6^1 - 3^0 - 3^1}$$

$$634 := \frac{6^0 + 3^5 + 4^5}{-6^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$635 := \frac{6^5 + 3^6 + 5^6}{6^1 + 3^3 + 5^1}$$

$$635 := \frac{6^5 + 3^6 + 5^6}{6^1 + 3^3 + 5^1}$$

$$637 := \frac{6^4 + 3^3 - 7^2}{-6^1 + 3^0 + 7^1}$$

$$638 := \frac{6^6 - 3^4 - 8^0}{6^1 + 3^1 + 8^2}$$

$$639 := \frac{6^4 - 3^2 - 9^1}{-6^1 - 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$640 := \frac{6^4 - 4^2 + 0^1}{6^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$$

$$642 := \frac{6^4 - 4^1 - 2^3}{-6^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$643 := \frac{6^6 + 4^4 + 3^3}{6^1 + 4^3 + 3^1}$$

$$643 := \frac{6^6 + 4^4 + 3^3}{6^1 + 4^3 + 3^1}$$

$$644 := \frac{6^4 - 4^1 - 4^1}{-6^0 - 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$645 := \frac{6^2 - 4^2 + 5^4}{-6^0 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$646 := \frac{-6^3 + 4^6 - 6^4}{-6^0 - 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$647 := \frac{6^4 - 4^0 - 7^0}{-6^0 + 4^1 - 7^0}$$

$$648 := \frac{6^4 - 4^0 + 8^0}{-6^0 + 4^1 - 8^0}$$

$$649 := \frac{6^1 + 4^1 + 9^5}{6^1 + 4^1 + 9^2}$$

$$649 := \frac{6^1 + 4^1 + 9^5}{6^1 + 4^1 + 9^2}$$

$$650 := \frac{6^4 + 5^1 - 0^0}{6^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$651 := \frac{6^4 + 5^1 + 1^0}{6^1 - 5^1 + 1^0}$$

$$653 := \frac{6^0 + 5^4 + 3^3}{-6^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$654 := \frac{-6^5 + 5^6 - 4^0}{6^1 + 5^1 + 4^0}$$

$$657 := \frac{6^4 + 5^2 - 7^1}{-6^1 + 5^0 + 7^1}$$

$$659 := \frac{-6^2 + 5^4 + 9^3}{-6^1 - 5^0 + 9^1}$$

$$662 := \frac{6^2 + 6^4 - 2^3}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$663 := \frac{-6^2 + 6^4 + 3^6}{6^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$664 := \frac{6^2 + 6^4 - 4^1}{-6^0 - 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$665 := \frac{-6^1 + 6^4 - 5^4}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$672 := \frac{6^4 + 7^2 - 2^0}{-6^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$673 := \frac{6^4 + 7^2 + 3^0}{6^1 - 7^0 - 3^1}$$

$$675 := \frac{6^0 + 7^2 + 5^4}{-6^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$677 := \frac{-6^2 + 7^3 + 7^4}{6^1 - 7^0 - 7^0}$$

$$679 := \frac{-6^0 - 7^2 + 9^3}{-6^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$680 := \frac{6^4 + 8^2 + 0^1}{6^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$680 := \frac{6^4 + 8^2 + 0^1}{6^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$682 := \frac{6^4 + 8^2 + 2^{12}}{6^1 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$682 := \frac{6^4 + 8^2 + 2^{12}}{6^1 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$683 := \frac{6^0 + 8^4 + 3^0}{-6^0 + 8^1 - 3^0}$$

$$684 := \frac{6^4 + 8^1 + 4^3}{-6^0 - 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$685 := \frac{-6^4 + 8^4 + 5^4}{-6^0 + 8^0 + 5^1}$$

$$688 := \frac{-6^4 - 8^3 + 8^5}{6^2 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$689 := \frac{6^4 + 8^0 + 9^2}{6^0 - 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$692 := \frac{-6^2 + 9^3 - 2^0}{-6^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$693 := \frac{6^6 + 9^3 + 3^{11}}{6^3 + 9^2 + 3^3}$$

$$693 := \frac{6^6 + 9^3 + 3^{11}}{6^3 + 9^2 + 3^3}$$

$$694 := \frac{-6^2 + 9^3 + 4^0}{-6^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$695 := \frac{6^2 + 9^3 + 5^4}{6^1 + 9^0 - 5^1}$$

$$699 := \frac{6^7 + 9^3 + 9^5}{6^4 - 9^2 - 9^3}$$

$$703 := \frac{7^0 + 0^1 + 3^9}{7^0 + 0^1 + 3^3}$$

$$703 := \frac{7^0 + 0^1 + 3^9}{7^0 + 0^1 + 3^3}$$

$$713 := \frac{-7^2 + 1^0 + 3^7}{7^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$722 := \frac{7^4 + 2^0 + 2^{12}}{7^0 + 2^2 + 2^2}$$

$$722 := \frac{7^4 + 2^0 + 2^{12}}{7^0 + 2^2 + 2^2}$$

$$723 := \frac{-7^1 + 2^0 + 3^6}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$724 := \frac{-7^4 + 2^{13} + 4^0}{-7^0 + 2^3 + 4^0}$$

$$725 := \frac{-7^4 + 2^0 + 5^5}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 5^0}$$

$$727 := \frac{7^3 - 2^{13} + 7^7}{7^2 + 2^{10} + 7^2}$$

$$728 := \frac{7^4 - 2^0 + 8^3}{7^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$729 := \frac{-7^0 + 2^0 + 9^3}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 9^0}$$

$$730 := \frac{7^0 + 3^6 + 0^1}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 0^0}$$

$$731 := \frac{7^0 + 3^6 + 1^0}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$732 := \frac{7^0 + 3^7 + 2^3}{7^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$732 := \frac{7^0 + 3^7 + 2^3}{7^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$733 := \frac{7^0 + 3^1 + 3^6}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$734 := \frac{7^0 + 3^6 + 4^1}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$735 := \frac{7^2 + 3^8 + 5^1}{7^0 + 3^1 + 5^1}$$

$$735 := \frac{7^2 + 3^8 + 5^1}{7^0 + 3^1 + 5^1}$$

$$736 := \frac{7^1 + 3^{10} + 6^4}{7^2 + 3^3 + 6^1}$$

$$736 := \frac{7^1 + 3^{10} + 6^4}{7^2 + 3^3 + 6^1}$$

$$737 := \frac{7^0 + 3^6 + 7^1}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$738 := \frac{7^0 + 3^6 + 8^1}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$739 := \frac{7^0 + 3^2 + 9^3}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$740 := \frac{7^3 + 4^6 + 0^0}{7^0 + 4^1 + 0^0}$$

$$740 := \frac{7^3 + 4^6 + 0^0}{7^0 + 4^1 + 0^0}$$

$$743 := \frac{7^5 + 4^5 + 3^0}{7^1 + 4^2 + 3^0}$$

$$743 := \frac{7^5 + 4^5 + 3^0}{7^1 + 4^2 + 3^0}$$

$$745 := \frac{7^0 + 4^7 + 5^1}{7^0 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$745 := \frac{7^0 + 4^7 + 5^1}{7^0 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$746 := \frac{7^3 - 4^0 + 6^6}{-7^1 + 4^3 + 6^1}$$

$$747 := \frac{7^0 + 4^7 + 7^2}{-7^0 + 4^2 + 7^1}$$

$$748 := \frac{-7^3 - 4^0 + 8^6}{7^3 - 4^0 + 8^1}$$

$$749 := \frac{7^1 + 4^9 - 9^0}{7^3 + 4^2 - 9^1}$$

$$752 := \frac{-7^0 + 5^4 + 2^7}{-7^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$753 := \frac{7^6 + 5^8 + 3^0}{7^2 + 5^4 + 3^0}$$

$$753 := \frac{7^6 + 5^8 + 3^0}{7^2 + 5^4 + 3^0}$$

$$754 := \frac{7^5 - 5^6 + 4^6}{7^0 + 5^1 + 4^0}$$

$$757 := \frac{-7^0 + 5^7 - 7^5}{7^1 + 5^2 + 7^2}$$

$$758 := \frac{-7^2 - 5^3 + 8^5}{7^2 - 5^1 - 8^0}$$

$$759 := \frac{7^4 - 5^3 + 9^0}{7^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$762 := \frac{-7^0 - 6^0 + 2^{15}}{-7^0 + 6^2 + 2^3}$$

$$763 := \frac{-7^4 + 6^5 + 3^6}{7^0 + 6^1 + 3^0}$$

$$763 := \frac{7^6 - 6^6 + 3^6}{7^2 + 6^2 + 3^2}$$

$$765 := \frac{-7^0 + 6^5 - 5^3}{-7^0 + 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$768 := \frac{-7^4 + 6^5 + 8^0}{7^1 - 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$769 := \frac{-7^5 + 6^9 - 9^6}{-7^0 - 6^6 + 9^5}$$

$$772 := \frac{7^2 + 7^5 + 2^7}{7^1 + 7^1 + 2^3}$$

$$772 := \frac{7^2 + 7^5 + 2^7}{7^1 + 7^1 + 2^3}$$

$$773 := \frac{-7^0 + 7^4 - 3^4}{7^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$775 := \frac{7^2 + 7^4 - 5^3}{7^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$776 := \frac{7^2 + 7^5 + 6^3}{-7^1 - 7^1 + 6^2}$$

$$778 := \frac{7^3 + 7^3 + 8^5}{-7^1 + 7^2 + 8^0}$$

$$779 := \frac{7^0 + 7^2 + 9^3}{-7^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$780 := \frac{-7^1 + 8^5 - 0^0}{7^2 - 8^1 + 0^0}$$

$$782 := \frac{-7^6 + 8^0 + 2^{19}}{7^1 + 8^0 + 2^9}$$

$$783 := \frac{-7^3 + 8^4 - 3^7}{7^0 - 8^1 + 3^2}$$

$$785 := \frac{-7^4 + 8^4 - 5^3}{-7^0 + 8^1 - 5^1}$$

$$792 := \frac{7^7 + 9^1 + 2^7}{7^1 + 9^1 + 2^{10}}$$

$$792 := \frac{7^7 + 9^1 + 2^7}{7^1 + 9^1 + 2^{10}}$$

$$793 := \frac{7^7 - 9^1 + 3^{13}}{7^4 - 9^2 + 3^6}$$

$$794 := \frac{7^0 + 9^3 + 4^3}{-7^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$795 := \frac{7^4 + 9^1 - 5^2}{7^0 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$796 := \frac{7^3 + 9^5 - 6^6}{7^0 + 9^1 + 6^1}$$

$$797 := \frac{-7^0 - 9^1 + 7^4}{7^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$798 := \frac{7^4 + 9^0 - 8^1}{7^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$799 := \frac{-7^4 + 9^2 + 9^5}{-7^0 - 9^1 + 9^2}$$

$$803 := \frac{8^4 + 0^1 - 3^4}{8^0 + 0^0 + 3^1}$$

$$803 := \frac{8^4 - 0^4 - 3^4}{8^1 - 0^1 - 3^1}$$

$$809 := \frac{8^1 + 0^1 + 9^5}{8^2 + 0^1 + 9^1}$$

$$809 := \frac{8^1 + 0^1 + 9^5}{8^2 + 0^1 + 9^1}$$

$$813 := \frac{-8^3 - 1^0 + 3^{10}}{-8^1 - 1^0 + 3^4}$$

$$819 := \frac{-8^1 - 1^0 + 9^4}{8^1 - 1^0 + 9^0}$$

$$820 := \frac{8^4 + 2^2 + 0^1}{8^0 + 2^2 + 0^1}$$

$$820 := \frac{8^4 + 2^2 + 0^1}{8^0 + 2^2 + 0^1}$$

$$821 := \frac{8^1 + 2^{12} + 1^0}{8^1 - 2^1 - 1^0}$$

$$822 := \frac{8^4 - 2^1 + 2^4}{8^0 + 2^1 + 2^1}$$

$$823 := \frac{8^4 + 2^4 + 3^1}{8^0 + 2^0 + 3^1}$$

$$823 := \frac{8^4 + 2^4 + 3^1}{8^0 + 2^0 + 3^1}$$

$$824 := \frac{8^2 + 2^5 + 4^7}{8^1 + 2^3 + 4^1}$$

$$824 := \frac{8^2 + 2^5 + 4^7}{8^1 + 2^3 + 4^1}$$

$$825 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{16} + 5^8}{8^3 + 2^4 + 5^2}$$

$$825 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{16} + 5^8}{8^3 + 2^4 + 5^2}$$

$$826 := \frac{8^4 - 2^1 + 6^2}{8^0 - 2^1 + 6^1}$$

$$827 := \frac{8^2 + 2^4 + 7^4}{8^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$827 := \frac{8^2 + 2^4 + 7^4}{8^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$829 := \frac{8^4 - 2^5 + 9^2}{8^1 - 2^1 - 9^0}$$

$$833 := \frac{8^5 + 3^0 + 3^{11}}{8^1 + 3^0 + 3^5}$$

$$833 := \frac{8^5 + 3^0 + 3^{11}}{8^1 + 3^0 + 3^5}$$

$$834 := \frac{8^5 - 3^5 + 4^0}{8^1 + 3^3 + 4^1}$$

$$835 := \frac{-8^3 + 3^7 - 5^1}{8^1 - 3^0 - 5^1}$$

$$836 := \frac{-8^4 + 3^{11} + 6^0}{-8^1 - 3^0 + 6^3}$$

$$837 := \frac{-8^3 + 3^7 - 7^0}{8^1 + 3^0 - 7^1}$$

$$838 := \frac{8^0 + 3^7 - 8^3}{8^0 + 3^2 - 8^1}$$

$$843 := \frac{8^2 - 4^6 + 3^8}{8^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$844 := \frac{8^3 - 4^2 + 4^7}{8^1 - 4^1 + 4^2}$$

$$845 := \frac{-8^0 + 4^4 + 5^5}{-8^0 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$846 := \frac{8^5 + 4^3 + 6^5}{8^1 + 4^1 + 6^2}$$

$$846 := \frac{8^5 + 4^3 + 6^5}{8^1 + 4^1 + 6^2}$$

$$847 := \frac{-8^0 + 4^6 - 7^4}{-8^0 + 4^1 - 7^0}$$

$$848 := \frac{8^2 + 4^7 + 8^3}{8^1 + 4^1 + 8^1}$$

$$848 := \frac{8^2 + 4^7 + 8^3}{8^1 + 4^1 + 8^1}$$

$$849 := \frac{8^3 + 4^4 + 9^2}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 9^0}$$

$$853 := \frac{-8^0 + 5^3 + 3^6}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$856 := \frac{-8^0 + 5^6 - 6^3}{-8^0 + 5^2 - 6^1}$$

$$857 := \frac{-8^1 + 5^4 + 7^6}{8^2 + 5^2 + 7^2}$$

$$859 := \frac{8^5 - 5^3 - 9^0}{8^2 - 5^2 - 9^0}$$

$$862 := \frac{8^4 + 6^3 - 2^1}{8^0 + 6^1 - 2^1}$$

$$863 := \frac{8^4 + 6^3 + 3^1}{8^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$$

$$863 := \frac{8^4 + 6^3 + 3^1}{8^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$$

$$864 := \frac{8^7 + 6^8 + 4^6}{8^2 + 6^3 + 4^6}$$

$$864 := \frac{8^7 + 6^8 + 4^6}{8^2 + 6^3 + 4^6}$$

$$865 := \frac{8^1 + 6^5 + 5^0}{8^1 + 6^1 - 5^1}$$

$$866 := \frac{-8^4 - 6^3 + 6^5}{-8^0 - 6^0 + 6^1}$$

$$872 := \frac{-8^0 - 7^3 + 2^{13}}{8^0 + 7^1 + 2^0}$$

$$873 := \frac{8^6 - 7^0 - 3^5}{8^1 + 7^2 + 3^5}$$

$$874 := \frac{8^0 - 7^4 + 4^7}{8^1 + 7^1 + 4^0}$$

$$875 := \frac{8^7 - 7^4 - 5^0}{-8^1 + 7^4 + 5^0}$$

$$876 := \frac{-8^0 + 7^4 + 6^6}{8^0 + 7^2 + 6^1}$$

$$879 := \frac{8^5 + 7^4 - 9^1}{-8^1 + 7^2 - 9^0}$$

$$892 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^3 + 2^{13}}{8^0 + 9^0 + 2^3}$$

$$893 := \frac{-8^3 + 9^5 + 3^7}{8^2 + 9^0 + 3^1}$$

$$895 := \frac{8^2 + 9^6 + 5^3}{8^3 + 9^2 + 5^0}$$

$$895 := \frac{8^2 + 9^6 + 5^3}{8^3 + 9^2 + 5^0}$$

$$896 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^4 + 6^5}{8^0 + 9^1 + 6^1}$$

$$897 := \frac{8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4}{8^1 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$897 := \frac{8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4}{8^1 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$922 := \frac{9^4 - 2^0 + 2^{13}}{-9^0 + 2^0 + 2^4}$$

$$923 := \frac{9^0 - 2^{10} + 3^8}{9^0 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$925 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{10} + 5^6}{9^0 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$925 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{10} + 5^6}{9^0 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$926 := \frac{9^3 + 2^{11} + 6^0}{9^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$926 := \frac{9^3 + 2^{11} + 6^0}{9^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$927 := \frac{9^4 + 2^3 + 7^6}{9^2 + 2^2 + 7^2}$$

$$927 := \frac{9^4 + 2^3 + 7^6}{9^2 + 2^2 + 7^2}$$

$$928 := \frac{9^4 - 2^0 - 8^2}{9^0 - 2^1 + 8^1}$$

$$932 := \frac{9^4 + 3^3 - 2^6}{-9^0 + 3^2 - 2^0}$$

$$933 := \frac{9^4 - 3^1 - 3^3}{9^0 + 3^1 + 3^1}$$

$$934 := \frac{-9^1 - 3^4 + 4^5}{-9^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$935 := \frac{9^2 + 3^6 + 5^3}{-9^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$936 := \frac{-9^1 + 3^6 + 6^3}{-9^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$937 := \frac{-9^0 + 3^8 - 7^0}{-9^0 + 3^0 + 7^1}$$

$$938 := \frac{9^4 - 3^1 + 8^1}{-9^0 + 3^2 - 8^0}$$

$$939 := \frac{9^1 + 3^1 + 9^4}{-9^0 - 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 942 &:= \frac{9^4 + 4^0 + 2^5}{9^0 + 4^1 + 2^1} \\
 942 &:= \frac{9^4 + 4^0 + 2^5}{9^0 + 4^1 + 2^1} \\
 943 &:= \frac{-9^2 + 4^6 - 3^5}{-9^0 + 4^1 + 3^0} \\
 944 &:= \frac{-9^2 + 4^0 + 4^5}{-9^0 + 4^0 + 4^0} \\
 945 &:= \frac{9^0 + 4^7 + 5^4}{9^1 + 4^1 + 5^1} \\
 945 &:= \frac{9^0 + 4^7 + 5^4}{9^1 + 4^1 + 5^1} \\
 946 &:= \frac{9^3 + 4^0 + 6^3}{-9^0 + 4^0 + 6^0} \\
 948 &:= \frac{9^4 + 4^5 - 8^0}{-9^0 + 4^0 + 8^1} \\
 949 &:= \frac{9^2 + 4^0 + 9^4}{-9^0 - 4^0 + 9^1} \\
 952 &:= \frac{9^4 - 5^2 + 2^7}{9^0 + 5^1 + 2^0} \\
 953 &:= \frac{-9^4 + 5^0 + 3^{11}}{9^2 + 5^3 - 3^3} \\
 954 &:= \frac{-9^2 + 5^6 - 4^6}{9^0 - 5^1 + 4^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 955 &:= \frac{9^4 - 5^0 + 5^3}{9^0 + 5^0 + 5^1} \\
 956 &:= \frac{9^4 + 5^3 + 6^1}{9^0 + 5^1 + 6^0} \\
 956 &:= \frac{9^4 + 5^3 + 6^1}{9^0 + 5^1 + 6^0} \\
 957 &:= \frac{9^4 + 5^4 - 7^4}{-9^0 - 5^0 + 7^1} \\
 958 &:= \frac{-9^5 + 5^0 + 8^6}{9^3 - 5^1 - 8^3} \\
 962 &:= \frac{-9^2 + 6^5 + 2^0}{9^0 + 6^1 + 2^0} \\
 963 &:= \frac{9^1 + 6^5 - 3^4}{9^0 + 6^1 + 3^0} \\
 965 &:= \frac{9^1 + 6^4 + 5^4}{9^0 + 6^1 - 5^1} \\
 967 &:= \frac{9^1 + 6^5 - 7^2}{9^0 + 6^1 + 7^0} \\
 968 &:= \frac{9^4 + 6^3 - 8^0}{9^1 - 6^0 - 8^0} \\
 969 &:= \frac{-9^3 + 6^7 + 9^8}{-9^4 - 6^5 + 9^5} \\
 972 &:= \frac{9^6 - 7^6 - 2^{15}}{9^2 + 7^3 - 2^5}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 973 &:= \frac{9^3 + 7^0 + 3^5}{-9^0 + 7^0 + 3^0} \\
 974 &:= \frac{-9^0 - 7^2 + 4^5}{-9^0 + 7^0 + 4^0} \\
 975 &:= \frac{9^5 + 7^4 - 5^6}{-9^0 + 7^2 - 5^0} \\
 976 &:= \frac{9^2 - 7^2 + 6^5}{9^0 + 7^0 + 6^1} \\
 978 &:= \frac{-9^4 + 7^5 + 8^3}{9^1 + 7^0 + 8^0} \\
 979 &:= \frac{9^2 + 7^6 + 9^3}{-9^1 + 7^2 + 9^2} \\
 983 &:= \frac{-9^4 + 8^6 - 3^1}{9^1 + 8^1 + 3^5} \\
 984 &:= \frac{9^3 - 8^0 + 4^4}{-9^0 + 8^0 + 4^0} \\
 992 &:= \frac{-9^0 + 9^8 + 2^7}{9^3 + 9^5 - 2^{14}} \\
 994 &:= \frac{9^1 + 9^3 + 4^4}{-9^0 + 9^0 + 4^0} \\
 996 &:= \frac{-9^4 + 9^5 + 6^4}{9^1 + 9^1 + 6^2}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.4 Four Digits Numbers

$$\begin{aligned}
 1021 &:= \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^{10} - 1^0}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 1^0} \\
 1022 &:= \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 2^1 + 2^{10}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^0 + 2^1} \\
 1023 &:= \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^{10} + 3^0}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 3^0} \\
 1024 &:= \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 4^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 2^0 + 4^1} \\
 1025 &:= \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{10} + 5^0}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 5^0} \\
 1026 &:= \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{12} + 6^1}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1026 &:= \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{12} + 6^1}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 6^0} \\
 1027 &:= \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{10} + 7^0}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 7^0} \\
 1028 &:= \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{11} + 8^1}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 8^0} \\
 1029 &:= \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{11} + 9^1}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 9^0} \\
 1032 &:= \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 2^{10}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^0 + 2^1} \\
 1034 &:= \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 4^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1035 &:= \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^9 - 5^5}{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^2 + 5^1} \\
 1036 &:= \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 6^0}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^3 - 6^1} \\
 1042 &:= \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 2^{10}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^0 + 2^1} \\
 1043 &:= \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 3^8}{-1^0 + 0^1 - 4^1 + 3^3} \\
 1052 &:= \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 2^5}{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 2^0} \\
 1062 &:= \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^2 + 2^{10}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1063 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 3^6}{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 3^0}$$

$$1064 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^6 - 4^6}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^2 + 4^1}$$

$$1072 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 7^2 + 2^{10}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1073 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^3 + 3^6}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1074 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^2 + 4^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$1083 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 8^2 + 3^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 3^1}$$

$$1087 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 7^6}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 7^2}$$

$$1092 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 9^4 - 2^3}{1^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 2^2}$$

$$1093 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 9^0 + 3^7}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1094 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^4 + 4^0}{1^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$1094 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^4 + 4^0}{1^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$1123 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^{12} - 3^6}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$1133 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 3^4 + 3^7}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1168 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 8^5}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 + 8^2}$$

$$1177 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^2 + 7^6}{1^2 + 1^2 + 7^2 + 7^2}$$

$$1177 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^2 + 7^6}{1^2 + 1^2 + 7^2 + 7^2}$$

$$1197 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 9^1 + 7^4}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$1216 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{12} + 1^0 + 6^6}{1^0 + 2^5 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$1219 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{14} + 1^0 + 9^5}{1^0 + 2^5 + 1^0 + 9^0}$$

$$1221 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{10} + 2^{15} + 1^0}{1^0 + 2^3 + 2^4 + 1^0}$$

$$1223 := \frac{1^0 + 2^3 + 2^{14} + 3^6}{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 3^2}$$

$$1223 := \frac{1^0 + 2^3 + 2^{14} + 3^6}{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 3^2}$$

$$1225 := \frac{1^0 + 2^7 + 2^{12} + 5^5}{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$1225 := \frac{1^0 + 2^7 + 2^{12} + 5^5}{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$1226 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 - 2^{12} + 6^5}{-1^0 - 2^0 - 2^0 + 6^1}$$

$$1227 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^6 + 2^{11} + 7^3}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$1229 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{13} + 9^0}{1^0 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 9^0}$$

$$1229 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{13} + 9^0}{1^0 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 9^0}$$

$$1230 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 3^8 + 0^1}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 0^0}$$

$$1230 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 3^8 + 0^1}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 0^0}$$

$$1232 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 2^9}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1233 := \frac{1^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 3^4}$$

$$1233 := \frac{1^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 3^4}$$

$$1234 := \frac{1^0 + 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^5}{-1^0 - 2^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$1235 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^1}{1^0 - 2^1 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1236 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 3^5 + 6^3}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 6^0}$$

$$1236 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 3^5 + 6^3}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 6^0}$$

$$1237 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 3^8 + 7^2}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 7^0}$$

$$1237 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 3^8 + 7^2}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 7^0}$$

$$1238 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 8^3}{1^0 + 2^0 - 3^2 + 8^1}$$

$$1239 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^9 - 3^0 + 9^3}{1^0 - 2^1 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$1243 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 + 4^0 + 3^6}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 - 3^0}$$

$$1245 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{15} - 4^5 + 5^4}{1^0 + 2^2 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$1247 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{10} + 4^7 + 7^2}{1^1 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$1247 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{10} + 4^7 + 7^2}{1^1 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$1249 := \frac{1^0 + 2^6 + 4^9 + 9^2}{1^0 + 2^6 + 4^3 + 9^2}$$

$$1249 := \frac{1^0 + 2^6 + 4^9 + 9^2}{1^0 + 2^6 + 4^3 + 9^2}$$

$$1251 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 5^7 + 1^0}{-1^0 + 2^6 + 5^1 + 1^0}$$

$$1252 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 - 5^5 + 2^{14}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 2^3}$$

$$1253 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{12} + 5^5 + 3^8}{1^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 3^1}$$

$$1253 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{12} + 5^5 + 3^8}{1^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 3^1}$$

$$1253 := \frac{-1^6 - 2^6 + 5^6 + 3^6}{1^2 - 2^2 + 5^2 - 3^2}$$

$$1254 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 5^3 + 4^6}{1^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$1254 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 5^3 + 4^6}{1^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 1255 := \frac{1^0 + 2^6 + 5^4 + 5^6}{1^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 5^1} & 1271 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{14} - 7^4 - 1^0}{1^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 1^1} & 1287 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{17} - 8^2 + 7^7}{1^0 + 2^5 + 8^3 - 7^1} \\
 1256 := \frac{1^0 - 2^4 - 5^2 + 6^4}{-1^0 + 2^0 - 5^1 + 6^1} & 1272 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^8 - 7^1 + 2^{10}}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 7^0 + 2^1} & 1289 := \frac{1^0 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 9^3}{1^0 + 2^3 + 8^1 + 9^1} \\
 1257 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{14} + 5^1 - 7^2}{1^0 + 2^2 + 5^0 + 7^1} & 1273 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{10} + 7^1 + 3^5}{1^0 - 2^1 + 7^0 + 3^0} & 1289 := \frac{1^0 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 9^3}{1^0 + 2^3 + 8^1 + 9^1} \\
 1258 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{16} + 5^7 - 8^1}{-1^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 8^1} & 1274 := \frac{1^0 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 4^7}{1^0 + 2^0 + 7^1 + 4^1} & 1292 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 - 9^4 + 2^{14}}{1^0 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 2^2} \\
 1259 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{14} - 5^2 + 9^1}{1^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 9^1} & 1274 := \frac{1^0 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 4^7}{1^0 + 2^0 + 7^1 + 4^1} & 1293 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} - 9^3 - 3^3}{1^0 - 2^1 + 9^0 + 3^0} \\
 1260 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{14} - 6^1 + 0^0}{-1^0 + 2^3 + 6^1 + 0^1} & 1275 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 7^4 - 5^4}{-1^0 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 5^0} & 1293 := \frac{1^4 - 2^4 + 9^4 - 3^4}{1^1 - 2^1 + 9^1 - 3^1} \\
 1261 := \frac{1^0 + 2^2 + 6^7 + 1^0}{1^0 + 2^2 + 6^3 + 1^0} & 1276 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^6 + 7^4 + 6^3}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 6^0} & 1294 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 9^1 + 4^7}{1^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 4^2} \\
 1261 := \frac{1^0 + 2^2 + 6^7 + 1^0}{1^0 + 2^2 + 6^3 + 1^0} & 1277 := \frac{1^0 - 2^8 + 7^2 + 7^5}{1^0 + 2^2 + 7^0 + 7^1} & 1294 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 9^1 + 4^7}{1^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 4^2} \\
 1262 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 + 6^4 - 2^5}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 6^0 + 2^1} & 1278 := \frac{1^0 - 2^8 - 7^1 + 8^4}{1^0 + 2^0 - 7^1 + 8^1} & 1295 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} - 9^3 - 5^2}{1^0 - 2^1 + 9^0 + 5^0} \\
 1263 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{14} + 6^4 + 3^0}{1^0 + 2^2 + 6^1 + 3^1} & 1279 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 7^3 + 9^4}{1^0 + 2^2 + 7^0 + 9^0} & 1296 := \frac{1^0 - 2^1 + 9^0 + 6^4}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 9^1 - 6^1} \\
 1263 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{14} + 6^4 + 3^0}{1^0 + 2^2 + 6^1 + 3^1} & 1279 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 7^3 + 9^4}{1^0 + 2^2 + 7^0 + 9^0} & 1297 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{10} - 9^2 + 7^4}{1^0 - 2^1 + 9^0 + 7^0} \\
 1264 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^5 + 6^4 + 4^0}{-1^0 - 2^0 - 6^0 + 4^1} & 1280 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{11} + 8^3 + 0^0}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 0^0} & 1298 := \frac{1^0 - 2^3 + 9^4 - 8^2}{1^0 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 8^0} \\
 1265 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 6^2 + 5^6}{1^1 + 2^1 + 6^1 + 5^1} & 1281 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 8^3 + 1^0}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 1^0} & 1299 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^4 - 9^2 + 9^4}{1^0 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 9^0} \\
 1265 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 6^2 + 5^6}{1^1 + 2^1 + 6^1 + 5^1} & 1282 := \frac{1^0 + 2^8 + 8^0 + 2^{10}}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 8^0 + 2^1} & 1305 := \frac{-1^0 + 3^8 + 0^1 + 5^6}{1^0 - 3^2 + 0^1 + 5^2} \\
 1266 := \frac{1^0 - 2^5 + 6^0 + 6^4}{1^0 - 2^1 + 6^0 + 6^0} & 1283 := \frac{1^0 - 2^8 + 8^5 - 3^9}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 3^2} & 1306 := \frac{1^0 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 6^4}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 6^0} \\
 1267 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^7 + 6^1 + 7^4}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 7^0} & 1285 := \frac{1^0 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 5^4}{1^0 + 2^4 + 8^1 + 5^0} & 1308 := \frac{1^0 + 3^9 + 0^1 - 8^2}{-1^0 + 3^2 - 0^0 + 8^1} \\
 1268 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^0 + 6^7 + 8^4}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 6^3 + 8^1} & 1285 := \frac{1^0 + 2^4 + 8^5 + 5^4}{1^0 + 2^4 + 8^1 + 5^0} & 1312 := \frac{-1^0 + 3^8 - 1^0 + 2^0}{1^0 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 2^1} \\
 1269 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 + 6^4 + 9^3}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 9^0} & 1286 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 - 8^1 + 6^4}{1^0 - 2^1 + 8^0 + 6^0} & 1320 := \frac{1^0 - 3^6 + 2^{11} + 0^1}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 0^1}
 \end{array}$$

$$1321 := \frac{1^0 - 3^6 + 2^{11} + 1^0}{-1^0 - 3^0 + 2^1 + 1^0}$$

$$1322 := \frac{1^0 + 3^8 + 2^4 + 2^5}{1^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1322 := \frac{1^0 + 3^8 + 2^4 + 2^5}{1^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1323 := \frac{1^0 + 3^7 + 2^9 + 3^8}{1^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$1324 := \frac{1^0 + 3^1 + 2^{16} + 4^8}{1^0 + 3^4 + 2^0 + 4^2}$$

$$1324 := \frac{1^0 + 3^1 + 2^{16} + 4^8}{1^0 + 3^4 + 2^0 + 4^2}$$

$$1325 := \frac{1^0 + 3^7 + 2^9 + 5^7}{1^0 + 3^1 + 2^5 + 5^2}$$

$$1325 := \frac{1^0 + 3^7 + 2^9 + 5^7}{1^0 + 3^1 + 2^5 + 5^2}$$

$$1326 := \frac{1^0 + 3^8 + 2^5 + 6^2}{1^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$1327 := \frac{1^0 + 3^7 + 2^{15} + 7^6}{1^0 + 3^0 + 2^6 + 7^2}$$

$$1327 := \frac{1^0 + 3^7 + 2^{15} + 7^6}{1^0 + 3^0 + 2^6 + 7^2}$$

$$1328 := \frac{1^0 - 3^6 + 2^{11} + 8^1}{-1^0 - 3^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$1329 := \frac{1^0 + 3^4 + 2^1 + 9^4}{1^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$1329 := \frac{1^0 + 3^4 + 2^1 + 9^4}{1^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$1332 := \frac{-1^0 + 3^2 + 3^{11} + 2^0}{1^0 + 3^0 + 3^1 + 2^7}$$

$$1333 := \frac{1^0 + 3^4 + 3^7 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 3^2 + 3^2 + 3^3}$$

$$1333 := \frac{1^0 + 3^4 + 3^7 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 3^2 + 3^2 + 3^3}$$

$$1335 := \frac{1^0 + 3^3 + 3^7 + 5^5}{1^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1335 := \frac{1^0 + 3^3 + 3^7 + 5^5}{1^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1337 := \frac{1^0 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 7^6}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 3^4 + 7^1}$$

$$1342 := \frac{1^0 + 3^{14} + 4^{11} + 2^{11}}{1^0 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 2^7}$$

$$1342 := \frac{1^0 + 3^{14} + 4^{11} + 2^{11}}{1^0 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 2^7}$$

$$1343 := \frac{1^0 + 3^6 - 4^7 + 3^9}{-1^0 - 3^0 + 4^1 + 3^0}$$

$$1344 := \frac{1^0 + 3^{11} + 4^1 + 4^4}{1^0 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 4^3}$$

$$1344 := \frac{1^0 + 3^{11} + 4^1 + 4^4}{1^0 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 4^3}$$

$$1345 := \frac{1^0 + 3^5 + 4^8 + 5^3}{1^0 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$1345 := \frac{1^0 + 3^5 + 4^8 + 5^3}{1^0 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$1346 := \frac{1^0 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4}{1^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$1347 := \frac{1^0 + 3^6 + 4^{10} + 7^1}{-1^0 - 3^5 + 4^5 - 7^0}$$

$$1348 := \frac{1^0 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 8^3}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$1349 := \frac{1^0 + 3^5 + 4^5 + 9^2}{-1^0 - 3^0 + 4^1 - 9^0}$$

$$1352 := \frac{-1^0 + 3^6 + 5^4 - 2^0}{-1^0 - 3^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1353 := \frac{-1^0 - 3^6 - 5^5 + 3^8}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1354 := \frac{1^0 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 4^0}{1^0 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$1354 := \frac{1^0 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 4^0}{1^0 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$1355 := \frac{1^0 + 3^2 + 5^4 + 5^6}{1^0 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 5^1}$$

$$1355 := \frac{1^0 + 3^2 + 5^4 + 5^6}{1^0 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 5^1}$$

$$1356 := \frac{1^0 + 3^6 + 5^4 + 6^0}{-1^0 + 3^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$1357 := \frac{-1^0 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5}{1^0 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 7^1}$$

$$1358 := \frac{-1^0 + 3^9 + 5^6 + 8^0}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 5^2 + 8^0}$$

$$1362 := \frac{1^0 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 2^5}{1^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1363 := \frac{-1^0 + 3^4 + 6^7 - 3^9}{1^0 + 3^0 + 6^3 - 3^3}$$

$$1364 := \frac{1^0 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3}{-1^0 - 3^0 - 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$1365 := \frac{1^0 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 5^6}{-1^0 - 3^0 + 6^1 - 5^0}$$

$$1366 := \frac{-1^0 - 3^6 - 6^3 + 6^5}{-1^0 - 3^0 + 6^0 + 6^1}$$

$$1368 := \frac{1^0 + 3^3 + 6^2 + 8^5}{1^0 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 8^1}$$

$$1368 := \frac{1^0 + 3^3 + 6^2 + 8^5}{1^0 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 8^1}$$

$$1368 := \frac{-1^4 + 3^4 + 6^4 + 8^4}{1^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$1369 := \frac{1^0 - 3^2 + 6^4 + 9^2}{-1^0 - 3^0 - 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$1375 := \frac{-1^0 + 3^9 - 7^5 - 5^3}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1377 := \frac{1^0 + 3^2 + 7^3 + 7^4}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$1382 := \frac{1^0 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 2^{15}}{1^0 + 3^3 + 8^1 + 2^1}$$

$$1382 := \frac{1^0 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 2^{15}}{1^0 + 3^3 + 8^1 + 2^1}$$

$$1383 := \frac{-1^0 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 3^3}{-1^0 - 3^0 + 8^1 - 3^1}$$

$$1384 := \frac{1^0 - 3^2 + 8^2 + 4^6}{-1^0 - 3^0 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$1385 := \frac{1^0 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 5^6}{1^0 + 3^0 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$1385 := \frac{1^0 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 5^6}{1^0 + 3^0 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$1386 := \frac{1^0 + 3^3 + 8^3 + 6^5}{1^0 + 3^1 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$1387 := \frac{-1^0 - 3^9 + 8^3 + 7^6}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 8^2 + 7^1}$$

$$1388 := \frac{1^0 + 3^1 + 8^2 + 8^4}{-1^0 - 3^1 - 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$1389 := \frac{-1^0 - 3^2 + 8^4 + 9^2}{1^0 + 3^0 - 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$1395 := \frac{-1^0 + 3^7 + 9^3 - 5^3}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1396 := \frac{1^0 + 3^8 + 9^5 + 6^0}{1^0 + 3^0 + 9^1 + 6^2}$$

$$1396 := \frac{1^0 + 3^8 + 9^5 + 6^0}{1^0 + 3^0 + 9^1 + 6^2}$$

$$1397 := \frac{-1^0 + 3^9 - 9^2 - 7^5}{-1^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$1403 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^7 - 0^0 - 3^8}{1^0 + 4^1 + 0^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1406 := \frac{-1^0 - 4^4 - 0^0 + 6^6}{-1^0 - 4^0 - 0^0 + 6^2}$$

$$1408 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^7 + 0^0 + 8^3}{-1^0 + 4^1 + 0^0 + 8^1}$$

$$1422 := \frac{1^0 + 4^0 - 2^6 + 2^{15}}{1^0 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 2^4}$$

$$1423 := \frac{1^0 + 4^7 + 2^5 - 3^7}{1^1 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$1424 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^0 + 2^{15} - 4^2}{1^0 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 4^2}$$

$$1425 := \frac{1^0 + 4^0 + 2^{15} + 5^1}{1^0 + 4^0 + 2^4 + 5^1}$$

$$1425 := \frac{1^0 + 4^0 + 2^{15} + 5^1}{1^0 + 4^0 + 2^4 + 5^1}$$

$$1426 := \frac{1^0 + 4^0 + 2^7 + 6^4}{-1^0 - 4^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$1427 := \frac{-1^0 - 4^7 - 2^{15} + 7^6}{-1^0 - 4^0 + 2^0 + 7^2}$$

$$1429 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^3 + 2^{18} + 9^3}{1^0 + 4^3 + 2^7 - 9^1}$$

$$1432 := \frac{1^0 + 4^6 - 3^8 + 2^{13}}{1^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$1433 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^8 - 3^7 - 3^{10}}{-1^0 + 4^1 - 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1434 := \frac{-1^0 - 4^2 + 3^9 - 4^5}{-1^0 - 4^0 - 3^0 + 4^2}$$

$$1435 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^7 + 3^3 - 5^4}{1^0 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 5^1}$$

$$1436 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^6 - 3^1 + 6^3}{-1^0 - 4^0 - 3^0 + 6^1}$$

$$1437 := \frac{-1^0 - 4^0 + 3^9 - 7^5}{-1^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$1438 := \frac{1^0 + 4^6 + 3^6 - 8^3}{-1^0 - 4^0 - 3^1 + 8^1}$$

$$1439 := \frac{1^0 + 4^9 - 3^9 + 9^3}{-1^0 - 4^3 + 3^5 - 9^1}$$

$$1443 := \frac{1^0 + 4^6 + 4^9 - 3^6}{1^0 + 4^1 - 4^3 + 3^5}$$

$$1447 := \frac{1^0 + 4^5 + 4^8 + 7^0}{-1^0 - 4^0 - 4^0 + 7^2}$$

$$1449 := \frac{-1^0 - 4^3 - 4^5 + 9^5}{-1^0 + 4^2 + 4^2 + 9^1}$$

$$1452 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 2^{12}}{-1^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1453 := \frac{1^0 + 4^8 - 5^3 - 3^3}{1^0 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 3^3}$$

$$1454 := \frac{1^0 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 4^7}{1^1 + 4^1 + 5^1 + 4^1}$$

$$1455 := \frac{1^5 + 4^5 + 5^5 + 5^5}{-1^0 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1455 := \frac{1^5 + 4^5 + 5^5 + 5^5}{1^1 + 4^1 + 5^1 - 5^1}$$

$$1456 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^3}{-1^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$1457 := \frac{-1^0 - 4^4 + 5^4 + 7^6}{1^0 + 4^1 + 5^3 - 7^2}$$

$$1458 := \frac{1^0 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 8^4}{1^0 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 8^0}$$

$$1459 := \frac{-1^0 - 4^9 + 5^9 + 9^0}{1^0 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^1}$$

$$1460 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^3 + 6^6 + 0^0}{-1^0 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 0^0}$$

$$1462 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^0 + 6^6 + 2^7}{-1^0 - 4^0 + 6^2 - 2^1}$$

$$1463 := \frac{1^0 + 4^9 + 6^5 - 3^6}{-1^0 - 4^1 + 6^3 - 3^3}$$

$$1466 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^4 + 6^0 + 6^6}{1^0 + 4^0 - 6^1 + 6^2}$$

$$1467 := \frac{1^0 + 4^5 + 6^5 + 7^0}{-1^0 - 4^0 + 6^0 + 7^1}$$

$$1469 := \frac{1^0 + 4^8 - 6^3 - 9^4}{-1^0 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 9^0}$$

$$1472 := \frac{1^0 + 4^8 + 7^7 + 2^3}{1^0 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 2^8}$$

$$1472 := \frac{1^0 + 4^8 + 7^7 + 2^3}{1^0 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 2^8}$$

$$1473 := \frac{1^0 + 4^3 + 7^5 - 3^8}{1^0 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1474 := \frac{-1^0 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 4^6}{-1^0 - 4^0 + 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$1475 := \frac{1^0 + 4^4 + 7^3 + 5^6}{1^0 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 5^1}$$

$$1475 := \frac{1^0 + 4^4 + 7^3 + 5^6}{1^0 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 5^1}$$

$$1476 := \frac{1^0 + 4^1 + 7^5 + 6^6}{-1^0 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 6^2}$$

$$1477 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^6 - 7^1 + 7^3}{-1^0 + 4^1 - 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$1478 := \frac{-1^0 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4}{1^0 + 4^0 - 7^1 + 8^1}$$

$$1479 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^6 + 7^3 - 9^0}{-1^0 + 4^1 - 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$1483 := \frac{1^0 - 4^5 - 8^4 + 3^{11}}{1^0 - 4^3 - 8^2 + 3^5}$$

$$1485 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^9 - 8^1 - 5^6}{-1^0 + 4^4 - 8^2 - 5^2}$$

$$1486 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^7 - 8^0 - 6^2}{1^0 + 4^0 + 8^1 + 6^0}$$

$$1487 := \frac{-1^0 - 4^1 + 8^5 - 7^2}{-1^0 + 4^2 + 8^1 - 7^0}$$

$$1489 := \frac{1^0 - 4^6 + 8^3 + 9^4}{-1^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$1492 := \frac{1^0 - 4^1 - 9^3 + 2^{13}}{1^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1493 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^6 - 9^4 + 3^{11}}{-1^0 + 4^3 + 9^2 - 3^3}$$

$$1494 := \frac{1^0 + 4^{10} - 9^6 + 4^{10}}{-1^0 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 4^5}$$

$$1495 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^{10} - 9^4 + 5^0}{-1^0 + 4^3 + 9^1 + 5^4}$$

$$1496 := \frac{-1^0 - 4^5 + 9^3 + 6^5}{-1^0 - 4^0 + 9^0 + 6^1}$$

$$1497 := \frac{1^0 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 7^0}{-1^0 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$1498 := \frac{1^0 + 4^4 + 9^3 + 8^3}{1^0 + 4^0 - 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$1499 := \frac{-1^0 + 4^9 - 9^3 - 9^5}{-1^0 + 4^3 - 9^1 + 9^2}$$

$$1504 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^8 + 0^1 - 4^6}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 4^4}$$

$$1520 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^8 + 2^4 + 0^1}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 2^8 + 0^0}$$

$$1522 := \frac{1^0 + 5^8 + 2^1 + 2^{11}}{1^0 + 5^0 + 2^7 + 2^7}$$

$$1522 := \frac{1^0 + 5^8 + 2^1 + 2^{11}}{1^0 + 5^0 + 2^7 + 2^7}$$

$$1523 := \frac{1^0 + 5^3 + 2^{14} + 3^5}{1^1 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$1523 := \frac{1^0 + 5^3 + 2^{14} + 3^5}{1^1 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$1524 := \frac{1^0 - 5^2 - 2^{10} + 4^6}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$1525 := \frac{1^0 + 5^3 + 2^{10} + 5^6}{1^0 + 5^0 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$1525 := \frac{1^0 + 5^3 + 2^{10} + 5^6}{1^0 + 5^0 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$1526 := \frac{-1^0 - 5^2 + 2^8 + 6^4}{-1^0 - 5^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$1527 := \frac{1^0 + 5^7 + 2^{17} + 7^0}{1^0 + 5^0 + 2^7 + 7^1}$$

$$1527 := \frac{1^0 + 5^7 + 2^{17} + 7^0}{1^0 + 5^0 + 2^7 + 7^1}$$

$$1528 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^5 - 2^2 - 8^2}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$1529 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^7 - 2^6 - 9^2}{1^0 + 5^2 + 2^4 + 9^1}$$

$$1531 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^8 + 3^9 + 1^0}{-1^0 + 5^2 + 3^5 + 1^0}$$

$$1532 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^7 + 3^2 - 2^0}{1^0 + 5^2 + 3^2 + 2^4}$$

$$1533 := \frac{1^0 + 5^7 + 3^{10} + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 5^3 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1533 := \frac{1^0 + 5^7 + 3^{10} + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 5^3 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1535 := \frac{1^0 + 5^2 - 3^4 + 5^5}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1537 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^5 - 3^0 - 7^2}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$1538 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^6 - 3^5 - 8^0}{1^0 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 8^0}$$

$$1539 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^6 - 3^5 + 9^1}{1^0 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 9^0}$$

$$1542 := \frac{1^0 + 5^1 + 4^5 + 2^9}{-1^0 - 5^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1543 := \frac{1^0 + 5^6 - 4^6 - 3^6}{1^0 + 5^0 + 4^1 + 3^0}$$

$$1543 := \frac{1^6 + 5^6 - 4^6 - 3^6}{1^1 + 5^1 + 4^1 - 3^1}$$

$$1544 := \frac{1^0 - 5^4 - 4^3 + 4^8}{-1^0 - 5^1 - 4^2 + 4^3}$$

$$1545 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^2 + 4^8 + 5^7}{-1^0 + 5^1 + 4^3 + 5^2}$$

$$1546 := \frac{-1^0 - 5^1 + 4^4 + 6^4}{-1^0 - 5^0 + 4^1 - 6^0}$$

$$1547 := \frac{1^0 + 5^4 + 4^7 + 7^1}{1^0 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 7^0}$$

$$1547 := \frac{1^0 + 5^4 + 4^7 + 7^1}{1^0 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 7^0}$$

$$1548 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^2 - 4^5 + 8^4}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$1550 := \frac{-1^0 - 5^2 + 5^5 + 0^0}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 0^0}$$

$$1551 := \frac{1^0 - 5^2 + 5^5 + 1^0}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$1553 := \frac{1^0 + 5^0 + 5^8 + 3^6}{1^0 + 5^3 + 5^3 + 3^0}$$

$$1553 := \frac{1^0 + 5^0 + 5^8 + 3^6}{1^0 + 5^3 + 5^3 + 3^0}$$

$$1557 := \frac{1^0 - 5^1 + 5^5 - 7^1}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$1559 := \frac{1^0 + 5^0 + 5^5 - 9^1}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$1560 := \frac{1^0 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 0^1}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 0^0}$$

$$1561 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^5 - 6^0 - 1^0}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$1562 := \frac{1^0 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 2^5}{1^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1562 := \frac{1^0 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 2^5}{1^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1563 := \frac{1^0 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1}{1^0 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 3^1}$$

$$1563 := \frac{1^0 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^1}{1^0 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 3^1}$$

$$1564 := \frac{1^0 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 4^0}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$1565 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 5^5}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1566 := \frac{1^0 + 5^9 - 6^5 + 6^7}{-1^0 + 5^3 + 6^0 + 6^4}$$

$$1567 := \frac{1^0 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 7^1}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 7^0}$$

$$1568 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^2}{-1^0 - 5^0 - 6^0 + 8^1}$$

$$1569 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 9^3}{-1^0 - 5^0 - 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$1573 := \frac{1^0 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 3^3}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1575 := \frac{1^0 + 5^5 + 7^2 + 5^5}{1^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1575 := \frac{1^0 + 5^5 + 7^2 + 5^5}{1^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1579 := \frac{1^0 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 9^2}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$1582 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 2^5}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$1583 := \frac{1^0 + 5^4 + 8^4 + 3^3}{-1^0 - 5^0 + 8^1 - 3^1}$$

$$1584 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^4 - 8^2 + 4^5}{-1^0 - 5^0 - 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$1585 := \frac{1^0 + 5^1 + 8^6 - 5^4}{1^0 - 5^2 + 8^2 + 5^3}$$

$$1586 := \frac{1^0 + 5^4 + 8^4 + 6^2}{-1^0 - 5^0 - 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$1587 := \frac{-1^0 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 7^2}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$1589 := \frac{1^0 + 5^6 + 8^1 + 9^5}{-1^0 - 5^2 - 8^1 + 9^2}$$

$$1595 := \frac{-1^0 - 5^5 - 9^5 + 5^7}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$1596 := \frac{1^0 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 6^0}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 6^2}$$

$$1597 := \frac{1^0 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3}{1^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$1597 := \frac{1^0 + 5^6 + 9^0 + 7^3}{1^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$1599 := \frac{1^0 + 5^5 - 9^1 + 9^2}{-1^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$1622 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^4 - 2^0 + 2^{15}}{1^0 + 6^1 - 2^1 + 2^4}$$

$$1623 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^2 + 2^{10} + 3^7}{-1^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1625 := \frac{1^0 + 6^8 + 2^3 - 5^6}{1^0 - 6^1 + 2^{10} + 5^1}$$

$$1626 := \frac{1^0 + 6^0 + 2^{16} + 6^6}{-1^0 + 6^2 - 2^1 + 6^2}$$

$$1627 := \frac{1^0 + 6^1 - 2^9 + 7^6}{1^0 + 6^1 + 2^4 + 7^2}$$

$$1628 := \frac{-1^0 - 6^2 + 2^0 + 8^6}{1^0 + 6^3 + 2^3 - 8^2}$$

$$1629 := \frac{-1^0 - 6^0 + 2^{13} - 9^4}{-1^0 - 6^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$1631 := \frac{1^0 + 6^4 + 3^{10} + 1^0}{-1^0 + 6^2 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$1632 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^4 + 3^4 + 2^8}{-1^0 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1633 := \frac{-1^0 - 6^0 - 3^3 + 3^8}{1^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1634 := \frac{1^4 + 6^4 + 3^4 + 4^4}{-1^0 - 6^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$1635 := \frac{1^0 + 6^7 + 3^1 + 5^7}{1^0 + 6^3 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1635 := \frac{1^0 + 6^7 + 3^1 + 5^7}{1^0 + 6^3 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1636 := \frac{-1^0 - 6^5 + 3^{10} + 6^8}{-1^0 + 6^1 - 3^5 + 6^4}$$

$$1637 := \frac{1^0 - 6^2 - 3^6 + 7^4}{-1^0 - 6^1 + 3^0 + 7^1}$$

$$1638 := \frac{-1^0 - 6^2 + 3^7 - 8^3}{1^0 + 6^0 - 3^2 + 8^1}$$

$$1639 := \frac{-1^0 - 6^0 - 3^1 + 9^4}{1^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$1640 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^8 - 4^4 + 0^0}{-1^0 + 6^0 + 4^5 + 0^1}$$

$$1642 := \frac{1^0 + 6^0 + 4^2 + 2^{13}}{1^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1642 := \frac{1^0 + 6^0 + 4^2 + 2^{13}}{1^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1643 := \frac{1^0 + 6^1 + 4^1 + 3^8}{1^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1643 := \frac{1^0 + 6^1 + 4^1 + 3^8}{1^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1647 := \frac{1^0 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^2}{1^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 7^1}$$

$$1647 := \frac{1^0 + 6^2 + 4^7 + 7^2}{1^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 7^1}$$

$$1648 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^6 + 4^0 - 8^3}{-1^0 + 6^2 + 4^0 - 8^1}$$

$$1649 := \frac{1^0 - 6^6 + 4^6 + 9^5}{-1^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 9^1}$$

$$1652 := \frac{-1^0 - 6^3 + 5^5 + 2^{11}}{-1^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1653 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^6 + 5^6 + 3^7}{1^0 + 6^1 + 5^1 + 3^3}$$

$$1654 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 4^5}{-1^0 - 6^0 - 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$1655 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^5 - 5^3 + 5^4}{-1^0 + 6^1 - 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1656 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^4 + 5^6 + 6^4}{-1^0 + 6^0 + 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$1657 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^4 + 5^3 + 7^5}{-1^0 + 6^1 - 5^0 + 7^1}$$

$$1658 := \frac{1^0 + 6^5 + 5^0 + 8^3}{-1^0 - 6^0 - 5^0 + 8^1}$$

$$1659 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^2 + 5^6 - 9^3}{1^0 + 6^1 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$1662 := \frac{-1^0 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 2^{13}}{-1^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 2^5}$$

$$1663 := \frac{1^0 + 6^8 + 6^8 + 3^3}{1^0 - 6^1 + 6^4 + 3^6}$$

$$1664 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^0 + 6^6 - 4^3}{-1^0 + 6^0 - 6^2 + 4^3}$$

$$1665 := \frac{-1^0 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 5^0}{1^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 5^2}$$

$$1666 := \frac{-1^0 - 6^0 - 6^1 + 6^6}{-1^0 - 6^0 - 6^1 + 6^2}$$

$$1669 := \frac{1^0 - 6^1 + 6^6 + 9^2}{-1^0 - 6^1 + 6^2 - 9^0}$$

$$1672 := \frac{1^0 + 6^4 + 7^3 + 2^5}{-1^0 - 6^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1673 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^5 + 7^4 + 3^{14}}{1^0 - 6^4 - 7^4 + 3^8}$$

$$1674 := \frac{1^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 4^8}{-1^0 + 6^2 - 7^1 + 4^2}$$

$$1675 := \frac{-1^0 - 6^1 - 7^3 + 5^8}{-1^0 + 6^3 - 7^1 + 5^2}$$

$$1676 := \frac{1^0 + 6^2 + 7^3 + 6^4}{1^0 + 6^0 - 7^1 + 6^1}$$

$$1677 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^5 - 7^3 - 7^4}{-1^0 + 6^1 - 7^0 - 7^0}$$

$$1678 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^4}{1^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$1679 := \frac{1^0 + 6^1 + 7^4 - 9^3}{-1^0 - 6^1 - 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$1682 := \frac{1^0 + 6^3 + 8^0 + 2^{13}}{1^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1682 := \frac{1^0 + 6^3 + 8^0 + 2^{13}}{1^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1683 := \frac{-1^0 - 6^3 + 8^4 + 3^9}{-1^0 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 3^0}$$

$$1685 := \frac{-1^0 - 6^3 + 8^3 + 5^8}{-1^0 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$1687 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^5 + 8^6 + 7^0}{1^0 + 6^3 - 8^1 - 7^2}$$

$$1689 := \frac{1^0 + 6^5 + 8^5 - 9^1}{1^1 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$1692 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^3 + 9^4 - 2^3}{1^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$1693 := \frac{1^0 - 6^1 - 9^4 + 3^{10}}{-1^0 + 6^1 - 9^0 + 3^3}$$

$$1696 := \frac{1^0 + 6^1 + 9^4 + 6^3}{1^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$1696 := \frac{1^0 + 6^1 + 9^4 + 6^3}{1^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$1698 := \frac{1^0 + 6^6 - 9^5 + 8^5}{1^0 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 8^0}$$

$$1699 := \frac{-1^0 + 6^5 - 9^1 + 9^3}{-1^0 + 6^1 - 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$1722 := \frac{1^0 - 7^3 + 2^4 + 2^{11}}{-1^0 - 7^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1723 := \frac{1^0 + 7^0 + 2^{20} + 3^6}{1^0 + 7^3 + 2^8 + 3^2}$$

$$1723 := \frac{1^0 + 7^0 + 2^{20} + 3^6}{1^0 + 7^3 + 2^8 + 3^2}$$

$$1724 := \frac{1^0 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^7}{1^0 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 4^1}$$

$$1724 := \frac{1^0 + 7^3 + 2^9 + 4^7}{1^0 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 4^1}$$

$$1725 := \frac{1^0 + 7^0 + 2^{15} + 5^1}{1^0 + 7^0 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$1725 := \frac{1^0 + 7^0 + 2^{15} + 5^1}{1^0 + 7^0 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$1726 := \frac{1^0 + 7^5 + 2^7 + 6^7}{1^0 + 7^1 + 2^7 + 6^2}$$

$$1726 := \frac{1^0 + 7^5 + 2^7 + 6^7}{1^0 + 7^1 + 2^7 + 6^2}$$

$$1727 := \frac{-1^0 + 7^4 + 2^{14} + 7^6}{1^0 + 7^1 + 2^6 + 7^1}$$

$$1728 := \frac{1^0 - 7^4 + 2^5 + 8^4}{-1^0 - 7^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$1729 := \frac{1^0 + 7^0 + 2^{15} + 9^2}{1^1 + 7^1 + 2^1 + 9^1}$$

$$1729 := \frac{1^0 + 7^0 + 2^{15} + 9^2}{1^1 + 7^1 + 2^1 + 9^1}$$

$$1733 := \frac{1^0 + 7^3 + 3^3 + 3^8}{1^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1733 := \frac{1^0 + 7^3 + 3^3 + 3^8}{1^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$1735 := \frac{1^0 + 7^3 + 3^0 + 5^5}{-1^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1737 := \frac{1^0 + 7^3 + 3^6 + 7^4}{-1^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$1739 := \frac{1^0 + 7^2 + 3^3 + 9^5}{-1^0 - 7^0 + 3^3 + 9^1}$$

$$1742 := \frac{-1^0 - 7^2 - 4^4 + 2^{11}}{-1^0 - 7^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1743 := \frac{1^0 + 7^7 + 4^4 - 3^{11}}{1^0 - 7^3 - 4^2 + 3^6}$$

$$1744 := \frac{-1^0 + 7^4 + 4^3 + 4^5}{-1^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$1745 := \frac{-1^0 + 7^1 + 4^9 + 5^7}{-1^0 + 7^1 + 4^3 + 5^3}$$

$$1746 := \frac{-1^0 - 7^4 - 4^6 + 6^6}{-1^0 + 7^1 + 4^2 + 6^0}$$

$$1747 := \frac{1^0 + 7^0 + 4^7 + 7^5}{1^1 + 7^1 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$1747 := \frac{1^0 + 7^0 + 4^7 + 7^5}{1^1 + 7^1 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$1748 := \frac{-1^0 - 7^3 - 4^4 + 8^4}{-1^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$1752 := \frac{1^0 - 7^5 + 5^7 + 2^0}{1^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 2^5}$$

$$1753 := \frac{-1^0 + 7^5 - 5^1 + 3^6}{1^0 + 7^0 + 5^1 + 3^1}$$

$$1755 := \frac{1^0 + 7^6 + 5^3 + 5^9}{-1^0 + 7^5 - 5^0 - 5^6}$$

$$1756 := \frac{1^0 + 7^6 + 5^0 + 6^0}{-1^0 + 7^1 + 5^2 + 6^2}$$

$$1758 := \frac{-1^0 + 7^5 + 5^7 + 8^0}{-1^0 + 7^2 + 5^1 + 8^0}$$

$$1759 := \frac{-1^0 - 7^5 - 5^2 + 9^5}{-1^0 - 7^0 + 5^2 + 9^0}$$

$$1762 := \frac{1^0 + 7^5 + 6^6 - 2^5}{-1^0 - 7^0 + 6^1 + 2^5}$$

$$1765 := \frac{1^0 + 7^3 + 6^4 + 5^3}{1^0 + 7^0 - 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$1766 := \frac{-1^0 + 7^3 + 6^5 + 6^5}{1^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 6^1}$$

$$1768 := \frac{-1^0 - 7^3 - 6^3 + 8^4}{-1^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$1769 := \frac{-1^0 + 7^7 - 6^3 - 9^6}{-1^0 + 7^2 + 6^2 + 9^2}$$

$$1782 := \frac{-1^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 - 2^8}{-1^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 2^3}$$

$$1783 := \frac{1^0 - 7^1 - 8^2 + 3^9}{1^0 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 3^0}$$

$$1784 := \frac{1^0 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5}{1^0 + 7^1 + 8^0 + 4^0}$$

$$1784 := \frac{1^0 + 7^5 + 8^1 + 4^5}{1^0 + 7^1 + 8^0 + 4^0}$$

$$1785 := \frac{1^0 + 7^4 + 8^1 - 5^4}{-1^0 - 7^0 + 8^1 - 5^1}$$

$$1786 := \frac{1^0 - 7^4 + 8^5 - 6^1}{1^0 + 7^1 + 8^1 + 6^0}$$

$$1788 := \frac{-1^0 - 7^1 - 8^3 + 8^4}{-1^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$1792 := \frac{-1^0 + 7^4 + 9^4 - 2^0}{1^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1793 := \frac{-1^0 - 7^4 + 9^3 + 3^{10}}{-1^0 + 7^1 - 9^0 + 3^3}$$

$$1795 := \frac{1^0 - 7^1 + 9^4 + 5^4}{1^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1805 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^4 + 0^1 + 5^5}{1^0 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1806 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^3 - 0^0 + 6^4}{-1^0 + 8^0 + 0^1 + 6^0}$$

$$1816 := \frac{-1^0 - 8^3 + 1^0 + 6^5}{1^0 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$1820 := \frac{-1^0 - 8^1 + 2^{15} + 0^0}{1^0 + 8^0 + 2^4 + 0^1}$$

$$1821 := \frac{1^0 + 8^1 + 2^{15} + 1^0}{1^0 + 8^1 + 2^3 + 1^0}$$

$$1821 := \frac{1^0 + 8^1 + 2^{15} + 1^0}{1^0 + 8^1 + 2^3 + 1^0}$$

$$1822 := \frac{-1^0 - 8^0 + 2^4 + 2^{14}}{-1^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 2^3}$$

$$1823 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^5 + 2^7 - 3^4}{1^0 + 8^1 + 2^3 + 3^0}$$

$$1824 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^0 + 2^5 + 4^7}{-1^0 + 8^0 + 2^3 + 4^0}$$

$$1825 := \frac{-1^0 - 8^3 - 2^9 + 5^6}{1^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 5^1}$$

$$1826 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^6 - 2^{10} - 6^0}{1^0 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 6^1}$$

$$1827 := \frac{-1^0 - 8^3 + 2^{19} + 7^4}{1^0 + 8^1 - 2^6 + 7^3}$$

$$1829 := \frac{-1^0 - 8^1 - 2^9 + 9^5}{-1^0 + 8^1 + 2^4 + 9^1}$$

$$1832 := \frac{1^0 + 8^3 - 3^6 + 2^{11}}{-1^0 - 8^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1833 := \frac{1^0 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 3^{12}}{1^0 + 8^2 + 3^0 + 3^5}$$

$$1833 := \frac{1^0 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 3^{12}}{1^0 + 8^2 + 3^0 + 3^5}$$

$$1834 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^2 + 3^9 + 4^6}{1^0 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 4^0}$$

$$1835 := \frac{1^0 - 8^3 + 3^8 + 5^5}{-1^0 + 8^1 - 3^0 - 5^0}$$

$$1836 := \frac{1^0 + 8^5 + 3^5 + 6^2}{1^1 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 6^1}$$

$$1837 := \frac{1^0 + 8^3 + 3^8 + 7^5}{1^0 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 7^0}$$

$$1837 := \frac{1^0 + 8^3 + 3^8 + 7^5}{1^0 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 7^0}$$

$$1843 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^5 + 4^6 - 3^1}{-1^0 + 8^1 + 4^1 + 3^2}$$

$$1845 := \frac{1^0 + 8^1 + 4^{10} - 5^4}{-1^0 + 8^1 - 4^3 + 5^4}$$

$$1847 := \frac{1^0 + 8^3 + 4^{10} + 7^1}{-1^0 + 8^3 + 4^3 - 7^1}$$

$$1852 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^3 + 5^4 + 2^{16}}{1^0 + 8^1 + 5^2 + 2^1}$$

$$1853 := \frac{1^0 + 8^6 - 5^4 + 3^{10}}{-1^0 - 8^2 - 5^1 + 3^5}$$

$$1854 := \frac{-1^0 - 8^3 + 5^3 + 4^6}{-1^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$1855 := \frac{1^0 + 8^6 - 5^1 + 5^5}{1^0 - 8^1 + 5^2 + 5^3}$$

$$1856 := \frac{-1^0 - 8^2 + 5^4 + 6^4}{-1^0 + 8^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$1857 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^5 + 5^0 + 7^6}{-1^0 + 8^1 + 5^2 + 7^2}$$

$$1858 := \frac{-1^0 - 8^4 + 5^6 - 8^4}{1^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$1859 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^4 + 5^6 + 9^3}{1^0 + 8^1 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$1862 := \frac{1^0 + 8^4 + 6^0 + 2^{14}}{1^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 2^3}$$

$$1862 := \frac{1^0 + 8^4 + 6^0 + 2^{14}}{1^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 2^3}$$

$$1863 := \frac{1^0 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^6}{1^1 + 8^1 + 6^1 + 3^1}$$

$$1863 := \frac{1^0 + 8^5 + 6^2 + 3^6}{1^1 + 8^1 + 6^1 + 3^1}$$

$$1864 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^7 - 6^8 + 4^0}{-1^0 + 8^1 + 6^3 + 4^0}$$

$$1865 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^7 - 6^7 - 5^6}{1^0 + 8^4 - 6^1 - 5^5}$$

$$1866 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^0 - 6^2 + 6^7}{-1^0 - 8^2 - 6^0 + 6^3}$$

$$1867 := \frac{1^0 + 8^2 + 6^7 + 7^2}{1^2 + 8^2 + 6^2 + 7^2}$$

$$1867 := \frac{1^0 + 8^2 + 6^7 + 7^2}{1^2 + 8^2 + 6^2 + 7^2}$$

$$1872 := \frac{1^0 + 8^1 + 7^7 + 2^7}{1^0 + 8^2 + 7^3 + 2^5}$$

$$1872 := \frac{1^0 + 8^1 + 7^7 + 2^7}{1^0 + 8^2 + 7^3 + 2^5}$$

$$1873 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^4 + 7^6 + 3^0}{-1^0 - 8^1 - 7^1 + 3^4}$$

$$1874 := \frac{1^0 - 8^3 + 7^4 - 4^2}{-1^0 - 8^0 - 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$1875 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^2 + 7^5 + 5^1}{-1^0 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$1879 := \frac{-1^0 - 8^3 + 7^4 - 9^1}{-1^0 - 8^1 + 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$1887 := \frac{-1^0 - 8^0 - 8^3 + 7^4}{1^0 + 8^0 - 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$1892 := \frac{-1^0 + 8^5 + 9^2 + 2^{16}}{-1^0 + 8^2 - 9^1 - 2^1}$$

$$1893 := \frac{1^0 + 8^5 - 9^4 + 3^7}{-1^0 + 8^1 - 9^0 + 3^2}$$

$$1894 := \frac{-1^0 - 8^1 + 9^4 + 4^5}{1^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$1895 := \frac{1^0 + 8^5 + 9^4 + 5^6}{-1^0 + 8^2 - 9^1 - 5^2}$$

$$1896 := \frac{1^0 - 8^6 - 9^3 + 6^7}{1^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 6^1}$$

$$1897 := \frac{-1^0 - 8^3 + 9^1 + 7^4}{1^0 - 8^1 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$1898 := \frac{1^0 - 8^3 + 9^1 + 8^5}{-1^0 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$1922 := \frac{1^0 + 9^0 - 2^7 + 2^{11}}{-1^0 - 9^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1923 := \frac{1^0 - 9^1 - 2^8 + 3^7}{-1^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$1924 := \frac{-1^0 + 9^1 - 2^8 + 4^6}{-1^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$1925 := \frac{1^0 + 9^0 + 2^{11} - 5^3}{-1^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$1926 := \frac{1^0 + 9^4 + 2^9 - 6^4}{-1^0 - 9^0 - 2^0 + 6^1}$$

$$1927 := \frac{1^0 + 9^4 + 2^1 + 7^8}{1^0 + 9^2 + 2^9 + 7^4}$$

$$1927 := \frac{1^0 + 9^4 + 2^1 + 7^8}{1^0 + 9^2 + 2^9 + 7^4}$$

$$1928 := \frac{-1^0 + 9^3 + 2^{14} + 8^4}{1^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 8^1}$$

$$1929 := \frac{1^0 + 9^4 + 2^{15} + 9^5}{1^0 + 9^1 + 2^5 + 9^1}$$

$$1929 := \frac{1^0 + 9^4 + 2^{15} + 9^5}{1^0 + 9^1 + 2^5 + 9^1}$$

$$1935 := \frac{1^0 - 9^3 + 3^1 + 5^7}{-1^0 + 9^1 + 3^3 + 5^1}$$

$$1936 := \frac{-1^0 + 9^5 + 3^{10} - 6^0}{-1^0 - 9^0 + 3^3 + 6^2}$$

$$1937 := \frac{1^0 + 9^4 - 3^5 + 7^6}{-1^0 - 9^1 + 3^4 - 7^1}$$

$$1942 := \frac{-1^0 - 9^1 + 4^4 + 2^{15}}{-1^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 2^4}$$

$$1943 := \frac{1^0 - 9^3 - 4^1 + 3^8}{-1^0 - 9^0 + 4^1 + 3^0}$$

$$1944 := \frac{-1^0 + 9^6 - 4^5 - 4^9}{1^0 + 9^1 + 4^3 + 4^3}$$

$$1946 := \frac{1^0 - 9^1 + 4^2 + 6^5}{1^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$1947 := \frac{1^0 + 9^7 + 4^7 + 7^0}{-1^0 + 9^0 + 4^3 + 7^4}$$

$$1948 := \frac{-1^0 + 9^6 + 4^2 - 8^5}{-1^0 + 9^0 - 4^4 + 8^3}$$

$$1949 := \frac{-1^0 - 9^3 + 4^2 + 9^4}{-1^0 - 9^0 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$1952 := \frac{-1^0 - 9^1 + 5^6 + 2^0}{1^0 + 9^0 + 5^1 + 2^0}$$

$$1953 := \frac{-1^0 - 9^0 + 5^6 + 3^0}{1^0 + 9^0 + 5^1 + 3^0}$$

$$1954 := \frac{-1^0 + 9^1 + 5^6 - 4^0}{1^0 + 9^0 + 5^1 + 4^0}$$

$$1955 := \frac{1^0 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 5^6}{1^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 5^1}$$

$$1955 := \frac{1^0 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 5^6}{1^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 5^1}$$

$$1957 := \frac{-1^0 + 9^2 + 5^6 - 7^2}{1^0 + 9^0 + 5^1 + 7^0}$$

$$1962 := \frac{1^0 - 9^2 - 6^1 + 2^{11}}{-1^0 - 9^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1963 := \frac{1^0 - 9^1 - 6^3 + 3^7}{-1^0 - 9^0 + 6^1 - 3^1}$$

$$1964 := \frac{-1^0 - 9^3 + 6^1 + 4^8}{-1^0 - 9^0 + 6^2 - 4^0}$$

$$1966 := \frac{1^0 + 9^2 + 6^1 + 6^5}{1^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$1966 := \frac{1^0 + 9^2 + 6^1 + 6^5}{1^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$1967 := \frac{-1^0 + 9^1 + 6^7 + 7^7}{1^0 + 9^0 + 6^3 + 7^3}$$

$$1968 := \frac{1^0 - 9^2 + 6^7 - 8^6}{1^0 + 9^0 + 6^1 + 8^0}$$

$$1970 := \frac{1^0 + 9^5 + 7^2 + 0^0}{-1^0 + 9^2 - 7^2 - 0^0}$$

$$1973 := \frac{1^0 + 9^0 + 7^6 + 3^6}{1^0 + 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^2}$$

$$1973 := \frac{1^0 + 9^0 + 7^6 + 3^6}{1^0 + 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^2}$$

$$1975 := \frac{1^0 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 5^8}{-1^0 + 9^2 - 7^1 + 5^3}$$

$$1979 := \frac{-1^0 - 9^3 - 7^5 + 9^7}{-1^0 - 9^0 + 7^4 + 9^1}$$

$$1982 := \frac{-1^0 - 9^0 - 8^2 + 2^{11}}{-1^0 - 9^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$1984 := \frac{-1^0 + 9^0 - 8^3 + 4^7}{-1^0 + 9^0 - 8^1 + 4^2}$$

$$1986 := \frac{1^0 + 9^2 - 8^6 + 6^7}{1^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$1987 := \frac{-1^0 - 9^5 - 8^5 + 7^6}{-1^0 - 9^0 + 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$1989 := \frac{-1^0 - 9^2 - 8^3 + 9^4}{1^0 + 9^0 - 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$2013 := \frac{-2^0 - 0^0 - 1^0 + 3^{11}}{2^3 + 0^1 - 1^0 + 3^4}$$

$$2023 := \frac{2^0 + 0^0 + 2^{11} - 3^3}{-2^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$2024 := \frac{-2^3 + 0^1 + 2^{11} - 4^2}{-2^0 - 0^0 - 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2025 := \frac{2^{15} + 0^0 + 2^{20} + 5^1}{2^4 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 5^1}$$

$$2025 := \frac{2^{15} + 0^0 + 2^{20} + 5^1}{2^4 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 5^1}$$

$$2026 := \frac{-2^4 + 0^1 + 2^{11} - 6^1}{-2^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2027 := \frac{2^3 - 0^0 + 2^{12} - 7^2}{-2^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2028 := \frac{-2^3 + 0^1 - 2^5 + 8^4}{-2^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2029 := \frac{2^2 + 0^0 + 2^{14} + 9^6}{2^2 + 0^0 + 2^8 + 9^1}$$

$$2029 := \frac{2^2 + 0^0 + 2^{14} + 9^6}{2^2 + 0^0 + 2^8 + 9^1}$$

$$2032 := \frac{-2^3 + 0^0 - 3^2 + 2^{11}}{-2^0 - 0^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2033 := \frac{-2^7 + 0^0 - 3^3 + 3^7}{-2^0 + 0^1 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2034 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^0 + 3^0 - 4^2}{-2^0 - 0^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2035 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^0 + 3^4 + 5^8}{2^6 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 5^3}$$

$$2035 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^0 + 3^4 + 5^8}{2^6 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 5^3}$$

$$2036 := \frac{2^{20} + 0^0 + 3^{13} + 6^6}{2^4 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 6^4}$$

$$2036 := \frac{2^{20} + 0^0 + 3^{13} + 6^6}{2^4 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 6^4}$$

$$2037 := \frac{2^4 + 0^0 + 3^{10} + 7^1}{2^0 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 7^0}$$

$$2037 := \frac{2^4 + 0^0 + 3^{10} + 7^1}{2^0 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 7^0}$$

$$2038 := \frac{2^5 + 0^0 + 3^{10} + 8^4}{2^1 + 0^0 + 3^3 + 8^0}$$

$$2038 := \frac{2^5 + 0^0 + 3^{10} + 8^4}{2^1 + 0^0 + 3^3 + 8^0}$$

$$2039 := \frac{2^0 + 0^1 + 3^4 + 9^5}{2^0 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 9^0}$$

$$2039 := \frac{2^0 + 0^1 + 3^4 + 9^5}{2^0 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 9^0}$$

$$2040 := \frac{-2^4 - 0^0 + 4^6 + 0^0}{2^0 + 0^1 + 4^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2041 := \frac{-2^4 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 1^0}{-2^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2042 := \frac{-2^0 - 0^0 - 4^1 + 2^{11}}{-2^0 - 0^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2043 := \frac{-2^7 + 0^1 - 4^2 + 3^7}{-2^0 - 0^0 + 4^1 - 3^0}$$

$$2044 := \frac{-2^2 + 0^1 + 4^5 + 4^5}{-2^0 - 0^0 - 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2044 := \frac{-2^8 - 0^8 + 4^8 + 4^8}{2^6 - 0^6 + 4^6 - 4^6}$$

$$2045 := \frac{2^{18} + 0^1 + 4^{10} + 5^3}{2^9 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 5^3}$$

$$2045 := \frac{2^{18} + 0^1 + 4^{10} + 5^3}{2^9 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 5^3}$$

$$2046 := \frac{2^{10} - 0^0 + 4^5 - 6^0}{-2^0 - 0^0 + 4^1 - 6^0}$$

$$2047 := \frac{2^{10} + 0^1 + 4^5 - 7^0}{-2^0 - 0^0 + 4^1 - 7^0}$$

$$2048 := \frac{2^{10} + 0^1 + 4^5 + 8^4}{2^0 + 0^1 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2049 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^1 + 4^7 + 9^1}{2^2 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$2049 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^1 + 4^7 + 9^1}{2^2 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$2050 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}{-2^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2051 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^0 + 5^0 + 1^0}{-2^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2052 := \frac{2^1 + 0^0 + 5^3 + 2^{16}}{2^1 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 2^2}$$

$$2052 := \frac{2^1 + 0^0 + 5^3 + 2^{16}}{2^1 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 2^2}$$

$$2053 := \frac{2^{16} + 0^0 + 5^2 + 3^7}{2^0 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 3^3}$$

$$2053 := \frac{2^{16} + 0^0 + 5^2 + 3^7}{2^0 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 3^3}$$

$$2054 := \frac{2^{10} + 0^0 + 5^1 + 4^5}{-2^0 - 0^0 - 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2055 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^0 + 5^0 + 5^1}{-2^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$2056 := \frac{2^{13} + 0^0 + 5^2 + 6^1}{2^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2056 := \frac{2^{13} + 0^0 + 5^2 + 6^1}{2^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2057 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^0 + 5^7 + 7^2}{2^5 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2057 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^0 + 5^7 + 7^2}{2^5 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2058 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^0 + 5^0 + 8^1}{-2^0 - 0^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$2059 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^0 + 5^0 + 9^1}{-2^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2060 := \frac{2^{20} - 0^0 - 6^2 + 0^0}{2^9 - 0^0 - 6^0 - 0^0}$$

$$2062 := \frac{2^3 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 2^{15}}{2^0 + 0^0 + 6^1 + 2^3}$$

$$2062 := \frac{2^3 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 2^{15}}{2^0 + 0^0 + 6^1 + 2^3}$$

$$2063 := \frac{2^6 + 0^6 + 6^6 + 3^6}{2^3 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 3^2}$$

$$2063 := \frac{2^6 + 0^6 + 6^6 + 3^6}{2^3 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 3^2}$$

$$2063 := \frac{2^6 - 0^6 + 6^6 + 3^6}{-2^2 - 0^2 + 6^2 - 3^2}$$

$$2064 := \frac{2^9 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 4^6}{2^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2065 := \frac{2^7 + 0^0 + 6^3 + 5^7}{2^0 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 5^0}$$

$$2065 := \frac{2^7 + 0^0 + 6^3 + 5^7}{2^0 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 5^0}$$

$$2066 := \frac{2^{13} + 0^1 + 6^2 + 6^2}{2^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2066 := \frac{2^{13} + 0^1 + 6^2 + 6^2}{2^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2067 := \frac{2^{12} + 0^0 + 6^2 + 7^0}{-2^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2068 := \frac{2^2 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 8^4}{-2^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2069 := \frac{2^8 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 9^6}{2^5 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 9^1}$$

$$2069 := \frac{2^8 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 9^6}{2^5 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 9^1}$$

$$2072 := \frac{2^{16} + 0^0 + 7^5 + 2^{17}}{2^5 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 2^6}$$

$$2072 := \frac{2^{16} + 0^0 + 7^5 + 2^{17}}{2^5 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 2^6}$$

$$2073 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^1 + 7^{11} + 3^{13}}{2^{17} + 0^1 + 7^7 + 3^1}$$

$$2073 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^1 + 7^{11} + 3^{13}}{2^{17} + 0^1 + 7^7 + 3^1}$$

$$2074 := \frac{2^1 + 0^0 + 7^2 + 4^6}{-2^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2075 := \frac{2^0 + 0^1 + 7^6 + 5^4}{2^1 + 0^0 + 7^2 + 5^1}$$

$$2075 := \frac{2^0 + 0^1 + 7^6 + 5^4}{2^1 + 0^0 + 7^2 + 5^1}$$

$$2076 := \frac{2^{14} + 0^0 + 7^1 + 6^3}{2^0 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2076 := \frac{2^{14} + 0^0 + 7^1 + 6^3}{2^0 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2077 := \frac{2^{10} + 0^0 + 7^0 + 7^7}{2^2 + 0^0 + 7^2 + 7^3}$$

$$2077 := \frac{2^{10} + 0^0 + 7^0 + 7^7}{2^2 + 0^0 + 7^2 + 7^3}$$

$$2078 := \frac{2^{13} + 0^0 + 7^5 - 8^2}{2^1 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 8^1}$$

$$2079 := \frac{2^4 + 0^0 + 7^6 + 9^5}{2^1 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 9^2}$$

$$2079 := \frac{2^4 + 0^0 + 7^6 + 9^5}{2^1 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 9^2}$$

$$2080 := \frac{2^6 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 0^1}{2^0 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2080 := \frac{2^6 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 0^1}{2^0 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2081 := \frac{2^6 + 0^0 + 8^4 + 1^0}{-2^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2082 := \frac{2^7 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 2^{13}}{2^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$2082 := \frac{2^7 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 2^{13}}{2^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$2083 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^0 + 8^4 + 3^7}{2^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2083 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^0 + 8^4 + 3^7}{2^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2084 := \frac{2^9 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 4^3}{2^2 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 4^1}$$

$$2084 := \frac{2^9 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 4^3}{2^2 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 4^1}$$

$$2085 := \frac{-2^5 - 0^0 + 8^5 + 5^4}{2^1 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2086 := \frac{2^{11} + 0^0 + 8^0 + 6^2}{-2^0 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2087 := \frac{2^9 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 7^5}{2^3 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$2087 := \frac{2^9 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 7^5}{2^3 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 7^1}$	$2125 := \frac{2^7 + 1^0 + 2^{12} + 5^2}{-2^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 5^0}$	$2138 := \frac{2^5 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 8^4}{2^1 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$
$2088 := \frac{2^4 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 8^4}{-2^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 8^0}$	$2126 := \frac{2^0 + 1^0 + 2^{11} + 6^8}{2^3 - 1^0 - 2^9 + 6^4}$	$2139 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 3^2 + 9^2}{-2^1 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$
$2089 := \frac{2^9 + 0^0 + 8^6 + 9^5}{2^3 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 9^2}$	$2127 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 2^{13} + 7^7}{2^4 + 1^0 + 2^5 + 7^3}$	$2139 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 3^2 + 9^2}{-2^1 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$
$2089 := \frac{2^9 + 0^0 + 8^6 + 9^5}{2^3 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 9^2}$	$2127 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 2^{13} + 7^7}{2^4 + 1^0 + 2^5 + 7^3}$	$2143 := \frac{2^8 + 1^0 + 4^9 + 3^{10}}{2^2 + 1^0 + 4^3 + 3^4}$
$2092 := \frac{2^3 - 0^0 + 9^2 + 2^{12}}{-2^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$	$2129 := \frac{2^3 + 1^0 + 2^{19} + 9^5}{2^3 + 1^0 + 2^8 + 9^1}$	$2143 := \frac{2^8 + 1^0 + 4^9 + 3^{10}}{2^2 + 1^0 + 4^3 + 3^4}$
$2093 := \frac{2^{12} + 0^1 + 9^1 + 3^4}{-2^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$	$2129 := \frac{2^3 + 1^0 + 2^{19} + 9^5}{2^3 + 1^0 + 2^8 + 9^1}$	$2145 := \frac{2^9 - 1^0 + 4^5 + 5^6}{2^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 5^1}$
$2095 := \frac{2^6 + 0^1 + 9^6 + 5^4}{2^7 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 5^3}$	$2130 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 3^4 + 0^1}{-2^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$	$2145 := \frac{-2^7 - 1^7 + 4^7 + 5^7}{2^2 - 1^2 + 4^2 + 5^2}$
$2095 := \frac{2^6 + 0^1 + 9^6 + 5^4}{2^7 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 5^3}$	$2131 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 3^4 + 1^0}{-2^1 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 1^0}$	$2147 := \frac{2^6 + 1^0 + 4^{10} + 7^7}{2^9 + 1^0 + 4^2 + 7^3}$
$2096 := \frac{2^{10} - 0^0 + 9^4 - 6^4}{2^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 6^0}$	$2132 := \frac{2^1 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 2^{12}}{2^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$	$2147 := \frac{2^6 + 1^0 + 4^{10} + 7^7}{2^9 + 1^0 + 4^2 + 7^3}$
$2097 := \frac{2^{10} + 0^0 + 9^3 + 7^3}{-2^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 7^0}$	$2132 := \frac{2^1 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 2^{12}}{2^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$	$2149 := \frac{-2^0 - 1^0 - 4^5 + 9^5}{2^0 + 1^0 + 4^2 + 9^1}$
$2098 := \frac{-2^{13} + 0^0 + 9^6 + 8^7}{2^3 + 0^3 + 9^3 + 8^3}$	$2133 := \frac{2^9 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 3^{10}}{2^1 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 3^3}$	$2150 := \frac{2^{20} - 1^0 + 5^4 + 0^1}{2^9 + 1^0 - 5^2 + 0^1}$
$2099 := \frac{-2^8 + 0^0 - 9^1 + 9^4}{2^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 9^0}$	$2133 := \frac{2^9 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 3^{10}}{2^1 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 3^3}$	$2152 := \frac{2^7 + 1^0 - 5^2 + 2^{11}}{-2^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$
$2103 := \frac{2^{18} + 1^0 + 0^0 + 3^6}{2^7 - 1^0 - 0^0 - 3^0}$	$2134 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 3^4 + 4^1}{-2^0 - 1^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}$	$2153 := \frac{2^{19} + 1^0 + 5^3 + 3^{10}}{2^1 + 1^0 + 5^2 + 3^5}$
$2112 := \frac{2^6 - 1^0 + 1^0 + 2^{11}}{-2^0 - 1^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$	$2135 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 3^4 + 5^1}{-2^1 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$	$2153 := \frac{2^{19} + 1^0 + 5^3 + 3^{10}}{2^1 + 1^0 + 5^2 + 3^5}$
$2114 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 1^0 + 4^3}{-2^0 - 1^0 - 1^0 + 4^1}$	$2136 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 3^4 + 6^1}{-2^0 - 1^0 - 3^1 + 6^1}$	$2154 := \frac{2^6 - 1^0 + 5^7 + 4^9}{2^4 + 1^0 + 5^3 + 4^2}$
$2115 := \frac{2^7 + 1^7 + 1^7 + 5^7}{2^5 - 1^0 + 1^0 + 5^1}$	$2137 := \frac{2^9 + 1^0 + 3^{11} + 7^5}{2^1 + 1^0 + 3^4 + 7^1}$	$2155 := \frac{-2^{12} + 1^0 + 5^5 + 5^5}{-2^1 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 5^0}$
$2123 := \frac{2^{13} + 1^0 + 2^{16} + 3^9}{2^3 + 1^3 + 2^3 + 3^3}$	$2137 := \frac{2^9 + 1^0 + 3^{11} + 7^5}{2^1 + 1^0 + 3^4 + 7^1}$	$2156 := \frac{2^{12} - 1^0 + 5^0 + 6^3}{-2^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 6^0}$
$2123 := \frac{2^{13} + 1^0 + 2^{16} + 3^9}{2^3 + 1^3 + 2^3 + 3^3}$	$2138 := \frac{2^5 + 1^0 + 3^8 + 8^4}{2^1 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$	$2157 := \frac{2^9 + 1^0 + 5^7 + 7^6}{2^4 + 1^0 + 5^2 + 7^2}$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 2157 := \frac{2^9 + 1^0 + 5^7 + 7^6}{2^4 + 1^0 + 5^2 + 7^2} & 2179 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 7^2 + 9^2}{-2^1 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 9^0} & 2198 := \frac{-2^5 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 8^2}{2^0 + 1^0 + 9^1 - 8^1} \\
 2158 := \frac{-2^3 + 1^0 + 5^6 - 8^3}{2^2 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 8^0} & 2180 := \frac{2^3 - 1^0 + 8^7 + 0^0}{2^{10} + 1^0 - 8^2 + 0^0} & 2203 := \frac{2^4 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 3^8}{2^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 3^0} \\
 2159 := \frac{-2^9 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 9^0}{2^2 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 9^0} & 2183 := \frac{2^{13} + 1^0 + 8^3 + 3^3}{2^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 3^0} & 2204 := \frac{2^2 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 4^9}{-2^2 + 2^7 - 0^0 - 4^1} \\
 2162 := \frac{-2^0 + 1^0 - 6^1 + 2^{20}}{2^3 + 1^0 - 6^2 + 2^9} & 2183 := \frac{2^{13} + 1^0 + 8^3 + 3^3}{2^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 3^0} & 2205 := \frac{2^1 + 2^{13} + 0^0 + 5^4}{2^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 5^0} \\
 2163 := \frac{2^{13} + 1^0 + 6^3 + 3^5}{2^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 3^0} & 2184 := \frac{-2^3 - 1^0 + 8^5 + 4^0}{2^1 + 1^1 + 8^1 + 4^1} & 2205 := \frac{2^1 + 2^{13} + 0^0 + 5^4}{2^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 5^0} \\
 2163 := \frac{2^{13} + 1^0 + 6^3 + 3^5}{2^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 3^0} & 2185 := \frac{2^0 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 5^1}{2^0 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 5^1} & 2206 := \frac{-2^5 + 2^{14} + 0^1 + 6^4}{2^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 6^1} \\
 2165 := \frac{2^7 + 1^0 + 6^8 + 5^9}{2^8 + 1^0 + 6^4 + 5^3} & 2185 := \frac{2^0 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 5^1}{2^0 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 5^1} & 2207 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{12} + 0^1 - 7^4}{-2^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 7^0} \\
 2165 := \frac{2^7 + 1^0 + 6^8 + 5^9}{2^8 + 1^0 + 6^4 + 5^3} & 2186 := \frac{-2^7 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 6^7}{2^6 - 1^0 + 8^2 + 6^0} & 2208 := \frac{2^7 + 2^{13} + 0^1 + 8^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 8^0} \\
 2167 := \frac{2^{14} - 1^0 + 6^4 - 7^3}{-2^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 7^1} & 2187 := \frac{-2^6 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 7^3}{-2^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 7^0} & 2208 := \frac{2^7 + 2^{13} + 0^1 + 8^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 8^0} \\
 2169 := \frac{2^{13} - 1^0 - 6^0 + 9^5}{2^5 - 1^0 - 6^0 + 9^0} & 2189 := \frac{2^2 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 9^4}{2^0 + 1^0 - 8^1 + 9^1} & 2209 := \frac{2^0 + 2^6 + 0^0 + 9^4}{2^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 9^0} \\
 2172 := \frac{2^8 - 1^0 - 7^1 + 2^{12}}{-2^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 2^0} & 2190 := \frac{2^3 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 0^1}{2^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 0^1} & 2209 := \frac{2^0 + 2^6 + 0^0 + 9^4}{2^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 9^0} \\
 2173 := \frac{-2^3 + 1^0 - 7^1 + 3^7}{-2^1 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 3^0} & 2190 := \frac{2^3 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 0^1}{2^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 0^1} & 2213 := \frac{2^{13} + 2^{14} + 1^0 + 3^9}{2^1 + 2^3 + 1^0 + 3^2} \\
 2174 := \frac{2^6 - 1^0 + 7^6 - 4^8}{2^1 - 1^0 + 7^1 + 4^2} & 2192 := \frac{2^6 - 1^0 + 9^2 + 2^{11}}{-2^0 - 1^0 + 9^0 + 2^1} & 2213 := \frac{2^{13} + 2^{14} + 1^0 + 3^9}{2^1 + 2^3 + 1^0 + 3^2} \\
 2175 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 7^0 + 5^3}{-2^1 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 5^0} & 2193 := \frac{2^{19} + 1^0 + 9^8 + 3^{11}}{2^8 + 1^0 + 9^1 + 3^9} & 2214 := \frac{-2^0 + 2^{14} - 1^0 + 4^8}{2^2 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 4^2} \\
 2176 := \frac{-2^3 - 1^0 + 7^4 - 6^3}{2^0 + 1^0 - 7^1 + 6^1} & 2194 := \frac{2^{11} + 1^0 + 9^2 + 4^3}{-2^0 - 1^0 - 9^0 + 4^1} & 2215 := \frac{2^7 + 2^{16} + 1^0 + 5^8}{2^4 + 2^6 + 1^0 + 5^3} \\
 2177 := \frac{2^{16} - 1^0 - 7^0 - 7^4}{2^4 - 1^0 + 7^1 + 7^1} & 2195 := \frac{-2^1 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 5^2}{2^1 - 1^0 + 9^0 + 5^0} & 2215 := \frac{2^7 + 2^{16} + 1^0 + 5^8}{2^4 + 2^6 + 1^0 + 5^3} \\
 2178 := \frac{2^{13} + 1^0 + 7^1 + 8^3}{2^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 8^0} & 2196 := \frac{2^{12} - 1^0 + 9^2 + 6^3}{-2^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 6^0} & 2217 := \frac{-2^2 + 2^{12} - 1^0 + 7^3}{-2^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 7^0} \\
 2178 := \frac{2^{13} + 1^0 + 7^1 + 8^3}{2^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 8^0} & 2197 := \frac{2^5 - 1^0 + 9^4 - 7^0}{2^1 - 1^0 + 9^0 + 7^0} & 2219 := \frac{2^{10} + 2^{16} + 1^0 + 9^1}{2^2 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 9^1}
 \end{array}$$

$$2219 := \frac{2^{10} + 2^{16} + 1^0 + 9^1}{2^2 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2230 := \frac{2^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 0^1}{2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2240 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{13} + 4^4 + 0^1}{2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$2221 := \frac{2^8 + 2^{14} + 2^{16} + 1^0}{2^1 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 1^0}$$

$$2231 := \frac{2^1 + 2^{13} + 3^6 + 1^0}{2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2241 := \frac{2^7 + 2^{11} + 4^3 + 1^0}{-2^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 - 1^0}$$

$$2221 := \frac{2^8 + 2^{14} + 2^{16} + 1^0}{2^1 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 1^0}$$

$$2231 := \frac{2^1 + 2^{13} + 3^6 + 1^0}{2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2242 := \frac{2^3 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 2^{13}}{2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$2222 := \frac{2^1 + 2^3 + 2^4 + 2^{17}}{-2^0 - 2^1 - 2^1 + 2^6}$$

$$2232 := \frac{-2^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 2^7}{-2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2242 := \frac{2^3 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 2^{13}}{2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$2223 := \frac{2^2 + 2^6 + 2^8 + 3^9}{2^1 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2233 := \frac{2^1 + 2^{13} + 3^2 + 3^6}{2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2243 := \frac{2^4 + 2^{13} + 4^7 + 3^4}{2^1 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2224 := \frac{2^7 + 2^9 + 2^{13} + 4^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2233 := \frac{2^1 + 2^{13} + 3^2 + 3^6}{2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2244 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{13} + 4^2 + 4^4}{2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2224 := \frac{2^7 + 2^9 + 2^{13} + 4^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2234 := \frac{2^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^6}{2^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2244 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{13} + 4^2 + 4^4}{2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2225 := \frac{2^2 + 2^9 + 2^{14} + 5^5}{2^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2234 := \frac{2^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^6}{2^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2245 := \frac{2^{13} + 2^{17} + 4^2 + 5^6}{2^1 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 5^0}$$

$$2225 := \frac{2^2 + 2^9 + 2^{14} + 5^5}{2^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2235 := \frac{2^0 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 5^6}{2^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2245 := \frac{2^{13} + 2^{17} + 4^2 + 5^6}{2^1 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 5^0}$$

$$2226 := \frac{2^6 + 2^6 + 2^{14} + 6^4}{2^0 + 2^1 + 2^2 + 6^0}$$

$$2235 := \frac{2^0 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 5^6}{2^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2246 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{13} + 4^3 + 6^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2226 := \frac{2^6 + 2^6 + 2^{14} + 6^4}{2^0 + 2^1 + 2^2 + 6^0}$$

$$2236 := \frac{2^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^7}{2^0 + 2^4 + 3^4 + 6^2}$$

$$2246 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{13} + 4^3 + 6^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2227 := \frac{2^4 + 2^8 + 2^{17} + 7^2}{2^0 + 2^0 + 2^3 + 7^2}$$

$$2237 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{13} + 3^5 + 7^0}{2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2247 := \frac{2^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^5}{2^1 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$2227 := \frac{2^4 + 2^8 + 2^{17} + 7^2}{2^0 + 2^0 + 2^3 + 7^2}$$

$$2237 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{13} + 3^5 + 7^0}{2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2247 := \frac{2^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^5}{2^1 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$2228 := \frac{2^2 + 2^{14} + 2^{16} + 8^3}{2^1 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 8^0}$$

$$2238 := \frac{2^0 + 2^4 + 3^{14} + 8^4}{2^1 + 2^{11} + 3^4 + 8^1}$$

$$2248 := \frac{2^5 + 2^{13} + 4^4 + 8^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2228 := \frac{2^2 + 2^{14} + 2^{16} + 8^3}{2^1 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 8^0}$$

$$2238 := \frac{2^0 + 2^4 + 3^{14} + 8^4}{2^1 + 2^{11} + 3^4 + 8^1}$$

$$2248 := \frac{2^5 + 2^{13} + 4^4 + 8^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2229 := \frac{2^4 + 2^{14} + 2^{18} + 9^2}{2^2 + 2^3 + 2^5 + 9^2}$$

$$2239 := \frac{2^3 + 2^{13} + 3^3 + 9^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2249 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{15} + 4^7 + 9^4}{2^2 + 2^2 + 4^2 + 9^0}$$

$$2229 := \frac{2^4 + 2^{14} + 2^{18} + 9^2}{2^2 + 2^3 + 2^5 + 9^2}$$

$$2239 := \frac{2^3 + 2^{13} + 3^3 + 9^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2249 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{15} + 4^7 + 9^4}{2^2 + 2^2 + 4^2 + 9^0}$$

$$2230 := \frac{2^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 0^1}{2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2240 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{13} + 4^4 + 0^1}{2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$2250 := \frac{-2^1 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 0^0}{2^0 + 2^0 + 5^1 + 0^1}$$

$$2251 := \frac{2^5 + 2^{14} + 5^7 + 1^0}{2^2 + 2^5 + 5^1 + 1^0}$$

$$2251 := \frac{2^5 + 2^{14} + 5^7 + 1^0}{2^2 + 2^5 + 5^1 + 1^0}$$

$$2252 := \frac{-2^0 - 2^6 + 5^6 - 2^{11}}{2^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2253 := \frac{2^0 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 3^4}{2^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 3^1}$$

$$2254 := \frac{2^0 + 2^{15} + 5^5 + 4^8}{2^1 + 2^1 + 5^2 + 4^2}$$

$$2254 := \frac{2^0 + 2^{15} + 5^5 + 4^8}{2^1 + 2^1 + 5^2 + 4^2}$$

$$2255 := \frac{2^6 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 5^6}{2^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2255 := \frac{2^6 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 5^6}{2^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2256 := \frac{2^{11} + 2^{12} + 5^4 - 6^0}{-2^0 - 2^0 - 5^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2257 := \frac{2^{12} + 2^{14} + 5^6 + 7^1}{2^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 7^1}$$

$$2257 := \frac{2^{12} + 2^{14} + 5^6 + 7^1}{2^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 7^1}$$

$$2258 := \frac{2^2 + 2^2 + 5^8 + 8^0}{2^3 + 2^5 + 5^3 + 8^1}$$

$$2258 := \frac{2^2 + 2^2 + 5^8 + 8^0}{2^3 + 2^5 + 5^3 + 8^1}$$

$$2259 := \frac{2^{11} + 2^{15} + 5^7 + 9^1}{2^2 + 2^5 + 5^1 + 9^1}$$

$$2259 := \frac{2^{11} + 2^{15} + 5^7 + 9^1}{2^2 + 2^5 + 5^1 + 9^1}$$

$$2260 := \frac{2^{11} + 2^{16} + 6^3 + 0^1}{2^3 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 0^1}$$

$$2260 := \frac{2^{11} + 2^{16} + 6^3 + 0^1}{2^3 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 0^1}$$

$$2261 := \frac{-2^1 + 2^{11} + 6^3 - 1^0}{2^0 - 2^1 + 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2262 := \frac{2^7 + 2^9 + 6^3 + 2^{13}}{2^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$2262 := \frac{2^7 + 2^9 + 6^3 + 2^{13}}{2^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$2263 := \frac{2^2 + 2^{14} + 6^5 + 3^6}{2^0 + 2^0 + 6^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2264 := \frac{2^7 + 2^7 + 6^5 + 4^5}{2^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2265 := \frac{2^1 + 2^{13} + 6^1 + 5^5}{2^0 + 2^1 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$2265 := \frac{2^1 + 2^{13} + 6^1 + 5^5}{2^0 + 2^1 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$2266 := \frac{2^3 + 2^{16} + 6^7 + 6^7}{2^3 + 2^4 + 6^2 + 6^3}$$

$$2266 := \frac{2^3 + 2^{16} + 6^7 + 6^7}{2^3 + 2^4 + 6^2 + 6^3}$$

$$2267 := \frac{2^0 + 2^5 + 6^4 + 7^5}{2^1 + 2^2 + 6^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2267 := \frac{2^0 + 2^5 + 6^4 + 7^5}{2^1 + 2^2 + 6^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2268 := \frac{-2^2 + 2^{11} + 6^3 + 8^1}{2^0 - 2^1 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2269 := \frac{2^3 + 2^8 + 6^6 + 9^3}{2^1 + 2^2 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$2269 := \frac{2^3 + 2^8 + 6^6 + 9^3}{2^1 + 2^2 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$2270 := \frac{-2^1 - 2^7 + 7^4 - 0^0}{-2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2271 := \frac{-2^0 - 2^7 + 7^4 - 1^0}{2^0 - 2^1 + 7^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2272 := \frac{2^0 + 2^3 + 7^3 + 2^{16}}{2^1 + 2^2 + 7^1 + 2^4}$$

$$2272 := \frac{2^0 + 2^3 + 7^3 + 2^{16}}{2^1 + 2^2 + 7^1 + 2^4}$$

$$2273 := \frac{2^1 + 2^7 + 7^4 + 3^8}{2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2273 := \frac{2^1 + 2^7 + 7^4 + 3^8}{2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2274 := \frac{2^0 - 2^6 + 7^4 - 4^3}{-2^0 - 2^0 - 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2275 := \frac{2^8 + 2^9 + 7^5 + 5^4}{2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2275 := \frac{2^8 + 2^9 + 7^5 + 5^4}{2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2276 := \frac{2^0 + 2^{13} + 7^5 + 6^2}{2^0 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2276 := \frac{2^0 + 2^{13} + 7^5 + 6^2}{2^0 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2277 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{15} + 7^1 + 7^5}{2^2 + 2^2 + 7^1 + 7^1}$$

$$2277 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{15} + 7^1 + 7^5}{2^2 + 2^2 + 7^1 + 7^1}$$

$$2278 := \frac{2^2 - 2^7 + 7^4 + 8^0}{-2^0 + 2^0 - 7^1 + 8^1}$$

$$2279 := \frac{2^1 + 2^7 + 7^6 + 9^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 7^2 + 9^0}$$

$$2279 := \frac{2^1 + 2^7 + 7^6 + 9^3}{2^0 + 2^0 + 7^2 + 9^0}$$

$$2280 := \frac{-2^3 + 2^6 + 8^6 + 0^1}{-2^2 + 2^7 - 8^1 - 0^0}$$

$$2282 := \frac{2^1 + 2^7 + 8^3 + 2^{16}}{2^0 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 2^4}$$

$$2282 := \frac{2^1 + 2^7 + 8^3 + 2^{16}}{2^0 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 2^4}$$

$$2283 := \frac{2^6 + 2^{14} + 8^4 + 3^1}{2^0 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 3^1}$$

$$2284 := \frac{-2^3 - 2^5 + 8^3 + 4^6}{-2^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2285 := \frac{2^0 + 2^{13} + 8^3 + 5^7}{2^0 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$2285 := \frac{2^0 + 2^{13} + 8^3 + 5^7}{2^0 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$2286 := \frac{2^3 + 2^{13} + 8^1 + 6^6}{2^0 + 2^4 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2286 := \frac{2^3 + 2^{13} + 8^1 + 6^6}{2^0 + 2^4 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2287 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{10} + 8^5 + 7^0}{2^1 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2287 := \frac{2^9 + 2^{10} + 8^5 + 7^0}{2^1 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2288 := \frac{2^4 + 2^{10} + 8^3 + 8^5}{2^1 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$2288 := \frac{2^4 + 2^{10} + 8^3 + 8^5}{2^1 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$2289 := \frac{2^{11} + 2^{12} + 8^5 + 9^0}{2^2 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 9^0}$$

$$2289 := \frac{2^{11} + 2^{12} + 8^5 + 9^0}{2^2 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 9^0}$$

$$2290 := \frac{2^3 - 2^{12} + 9^5 - 0^0}{-2^0 + 2^4 + 9^1 + 0^1}$$

$$2291 := \frac{2^2 + 2^9 + 9^5 + 1^0}{2^3 + 2^3 + 9^1 + 1^0}$$

$$2291 := \frac{2^2 + 2^9 + 9^5 + 1^0}{2^3 + 2^3 + 9^1 + 1^0}$$

$$2292 := \frac{-2^0 + 2^5 + 9^5 + 2^9}{2^0 + 2^3 + 9^0 + 2^4}$$

$$2293 := \frac{2^3 + 2^{13} + 9^3 + 3^5}{2^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2293 := \frac{2^3 + 2^{13} + 9^3 + 3^5}{2^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2294 := \frac{2^0 + 2^{13} + 9^4 + 4^8}{2^0 + 2^5 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2294 := \frac{2^0 + 2^{13} + 9^4 + 4^8}{2^0 + 2^5 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2295 := \frac{2^2 + 2^{14} + 9^4 + 5^0}{2^1 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2295 := \frac{2^2 + 2^{14} + 9^4 + 5^0}{2^1 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2296 := \frac{2^8 + 2^{11} - 9^1 + 6^0}{-2^0 - 2^0 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$2297 := \frac{2^{11} + 2^{19} + 9^4 + 7^1}{2^4 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 7^1}$$

$$2297 := \frac{2^{11} + 2^{19} + 9^4 + 7^1}{2^4 + 2^7 + 9^2 + 7^1}$$

$$2298 := \frac{2^{10} + 2^{16} + 9^2 + 8^0}{2^2 + 2^3 + 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$2298 := \frac{2^{10} + 2^{16} + 9^2 + 8^0}{2^2 + 2^3 + 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$2299 := \frac{2^2 - 2^{11} + 9^2 + 9^4}{-2^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2300 := \frac{2^{17} + 3^3 + 0^0 + 0^1}{2^5 + 3^3 - 0^0 - 0^0}$$

$$2301 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^9 + 0^0 + 1^0}{2^2 + 3^1 + 0^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2301 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^9 + 0^0 + 1^0}{2^2 + 3^1 + 0^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2302 := \frac{2^8 + 3^7 + 0^0 + 2^{17}}{2^4 + 3^2 + 0^0 + 2^5}$$

$$2302 := \frac{2^8 + 3^7 + 0^0 + 2^{17}}{2^4 + 3^2 + 0^0 + 2^5}$$

$$2303 := \frac{-2^7 + 3^5 + 0^0 + 3^7}{-2^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 3^0}$$

$$2304 := \frac{2^2 + 3^{11} + 0^0 + 4^4}{2^2 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 4^3}$$

$$2304 := \frac{2^2 + 3^{11} + 0^0 + 4^4}{2^2 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 4^3}$$

$$2305 := \frac{2^8 + 3^{10} + 0^1 + 5^4}{2^4 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2305 := \frac{2^8 + 3^{10} + 0^1 + 5^4}{2^4 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2306 := \frac{2^{18} + 3^7 + 0^0 + 6^5}{2^0 + 3^4 + 0^1 + 6^2}$$

$$2306 := \frac{2^{18} + 3^7 + 0^0 + 6^5}{2^0 + 3^4 + 0^1 + 6^2}$$

$$2307 := \frac{2^4 + 3^8 + 0^0 + 7^3}{2^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2307 := \frac{2^4 + 3^8 + 0^0 + 7^3}{2^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2308 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^9 + 0^0 + 8^2}{2^2 + 3^1 + 0^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2308 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^9 + 0^0 + 8^2}{2^2 + 3^1 + 0^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2309 := \frac{2^8 + 3^6 + 0^1 + 9^5}{2^3 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 9^1}$$

$$2309 := \frac{2^8 + 3^6 + 0^1 + 9^5}{2^3 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 9^1}$$

$$2310 := \frac{2^{19} + 3^4 + 1^0 + 0^1}{-2^4 + 3^5 - 1^0 + 0^0}$$

$$2312 := \frac{-2^1 + 3^7 - 1^0 + 2^7}{-2^0 - 3^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2313 := \frac{2^7 - 3^0 - 1^0 + 3^7}{-2^1 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2314 := \frac{2^{17} + 3^4 + 1^0 + 4^8}{2^1 + 3^4 + 1^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2314 := \frac{2^{17} + 3^4 + 1^0 + 4^8}{2^1 + 3^4 + 1^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2315 := \frac{2^{15} + 3^8 + 1^0 + 5^2}{2^1 + 3^2 + 1^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2316 := \frac{2^{13} + 3^5 + 1^0 + 6^5}{2^1 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2316 := \frac{2^{13} + 3^5 + 1^0 + 6^5}{2^1 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2317 := \frac{2^7 + 3^7 + 1^0 + 7^0}{-2^1 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2318 := \frac{2^{11} - 3^5 + 1^0 + 8^3}{2^0 - 3^2 + 1^0 + 8^1}$$

$$2319 := \frac{2^{13} + 3^2 + 1^0 + 9^5}{2^4 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2319 := \frac{2^{13} + 3^2 + 1^0 + 9^5}{2^4 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2320 := \frac{2^2 + 3^3 + 2^{19} + 0^0}{2^4 + 3^4 + 2^7 + 0^0}$$

$$2321 := \frac{2^8 + 3^0 + 2^{19} + 1^0}{2^4 + 3^4 + 2^7 + 1^0}$$

$$2321 := \frac{2^8 + 3^0 + 2^{19} + 1^0}{2^4 + 3^4 + 2^7 + 1^0}$$

$$2322 := \frac{2^0 + 3^7 + 2^2 + 2^{14}}{2^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 2^2}$$

$$2322 := \frac{2^0 + 3^7 + 2^2 + 2^{14}}{2^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 2^2}$$

$$2323 := \frac{2^5 + 3^7 + 2^9 + 3^8}{2^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2323 := \frac{2^5 + 3^7 + 2^9 + 3^8}{2^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2324 := \frac{2^0 + 3^1 + 2^{16} + 4^9}{2^2 + 3^2 + 2^6 + 4^3}$$

$$2325 := \frac{2^2 + 3^7 + 2^{14} + 5^2}{2^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2325 := \frac{2^2 + 3^7 + 2^{14} + 5^2}{2^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2326 := \frac{2^0 + 3^7 + 2^{14} + 6^2}{2^1 + 3^0 + 2^2 + 6^0}$$

$$2326 := \frac{2^0 + 3^7 + 2^{14} + 6^2}{2^1 + 3^0 + 2^2 + 6^0}$$

$$2327 := \frac{2^{12} + 3^9 + 2^{12} + 7^2}{2^0 + 3^1 + 2^0 + 7^1}$$

$$2327 := \frac{2^{12} + 3^9 + 2^{12} + 7^2}{2^0 + 3^1 + 2^0 + 7^1}$$

$$2328 := \frac{2^2 + 3^{13} + 2^{16} + 8^0}{2^6 + 3^2 + 2^7 + 8^3}$$

$$2328 := \frac{2^2 + 3^{13} + 2^{16} + 8^0}{2^6 + 3^2 + 2^7 + 8^3}$$

$$2329 := \frac{2^6 + 3^9 + 2^{13} + 9^1}{2^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2329 := \frac{2^6 + 3^9 + 2^{13} + 9^1}{2^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2330 := \frac{2^{20} + 3^7 + 3^{11} + 0^1}{2^8 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 0^0}$$

$$2330 := \frac{2^{20} + 3^7 + 3^{11} + 0^1}{2^8 + 3^3 + 3^5 + 0^0}$$

$$2331 := \frac{2^{15} + 3^2 + 3^7 + 1^0}{2^1 + 3^1 + 3^2 + 1^0}$$

$$2331 := \frac{2^{15} + 3^2 + 3^7 + 1^0}{2^1 + 3^1 + 3^2 + 1^0}$$

$$2332 := \frac{2^2 + 3^4 + 3^7 + 2^{14}}{2^0 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 2^0}$$

$$2333 := \frac{2^6 + 3^5 + 3^7 + 3^{11}}{2^5 + 3^2 + 3^2 + 3^3}$$

$$2334 := \frac{2^1 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 4^6}{2^1 + 3^0 + 3^2 + 4^0}$$

$$2335 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^2 + 3^{11} + 5^6}{2^2 + 3^3 + 3^3 + 5^2}$$

$$2335 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^2 + 3^{11} + 5^6}{2^2 + 3^3 + 3^3 + 5^2}$$

$$2336 := \frac{2^{11} + 3^6 + 3^8 + 6^1}{2^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2337 := \frac{2^0 + 3^0 + 3^8 + 7^5}{2^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 7^1}$$

$$2337 := \frac{2^0 + 3^0 + 3^8 + 7^5}{2^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 7^1}$$

$$2338 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^2 + 3^8 + 8^4}{2^1 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2338 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^2 + 3^8 + 8^4}{2^1 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2339 := \frac{2^{16} + 3^3 + 3^7 + 9^2}{2^1 + 3^2 + 3^2 + 9^1}$$

$$2339 := \frac{2^{16} + 3^3 + 3^7 + 9^2}{2^1 + 3^2 + 3^2 + 9^1}$$

$$2340 := \frac{-2^0 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 0^1}{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 0^0}$$

$$2341 := \frac{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 1^0}{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 1^0}$$

$$2341 := \frac{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 1^0}{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 1^0}$$

$$2342 := \frac{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 2^3}{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 2^2}$$

$$2342 := \frac{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 2^3}{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 2^2}$$

$$2343 := \frac{2^{15} + 3^1 + 4^1 + 3^3}{2^0 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 3^2}$$

$$2344 := \frac{2^0 - 3^6 - 4^5 + 4^6}{-2^0 - 3^0 - 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2345 := \frac{2^6 + 3^7 + 4^7 + 5^3}{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2346 := \frac{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^2}{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2346 := \frac{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^2}{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2347 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^8 + 4^6 + 7^4}{2^0 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2347 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^8 + 4^6 + 7^4}{2^0 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2348 := \frac{2^{11} + 3^9 + 4^0 + 8^4}{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 8^1}$$

$$2348 := \frac{2^{11} + 3^9 + 4^0 + 8^4}{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 8^1}$$

$$2349 := \frac{2^7 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 9^2}{2^1 + 3^0 + 4^2 + 9^1}$$

$$2349 := \frac{2^7 + 3^3 + 4^8 + 9^2}{2^1 + 3^0 + 4^2 + 9^1}$$

$$2350 := \frac{2^{17} + 3^1 + 5^8 + 0^1}{2^4 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 0^1}$$

$$2350 := \frac{2^{17} + 3^1 + 5^8 + 0^1}{2^4 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 0^1}$$

$$2351 := \frac{2^{19} - 3^2 - 5^1 - 1^0}{2^4 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 1^0}$$

$$2352 := \frac{2^{11} + 3^7 + 5^5 + 2^{11}}{2^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$2353 := \frac{2^{14} + 3^0 + 5^1 + 3^4}{2^1 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 3^1}$$

$$2354 := \frac{2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 4^6}{2^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2354 := \frac{2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 4^6}{2^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2355 := \frac{2^4 + 3^9 + 5^0 + 5^6}{2^1 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2355 := \frac{2^4 + 3^9 + 5^0 + 5^6}{2^1 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2356 := \frac{2^3 + 3^7 + 5^4 + 6^6}{2^0 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$2357 := \frac{2^{16} + 3^3 + 5^3 + 7^5}{2^1 + 3^0 + 5^2 + 7^1}$$

$$2357 := \frac{2^{16} + 3^3 + 5^3 + 7^5}{2^1 + 3^0 + 5^2 + 7^1}$$

$$2358 := \frac{2^{11} + 3^8 + 5^7 + 8^3}{2^0 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 8^1}$$

$$2358 := \frac{2^{11} + 3^8 + 5^7 + 8^3}{2^0 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 8^1}$$

$$2359 := \frac{2^{14} + 3^1 + 5^3 + 9^0}{2^1 + 3^1 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2359 := \frac{2^{14} + 3^1 + 5^3 + 9^0}{2^1 + 3^1 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2360 := \frac{2^9 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 0^0}{2^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2360 := \frac{2^9 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 0^0}{2^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2361 := \frac{2^{16} + 3^2 - 6^6 - 1^0}{-2^0 + 3^2 - 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2362 := \frac{2^0 + 3^{11} + 6^0 + 2^0}{2^0 + 3^2 + 6^0 + 2^6}$$

$$2362 := \frac{2^0 + 3^{11} + 6^0 + 2^0}{2^0 + 3^2 + 6^0 + 2^6}$$

$$2363 := \frac{2^4 + 3^2 + 6^0 + 3^{10}}{2^0 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 3^2}$$

$$2363 := \frac{2^4 + 3^2 + 6^0 + 3^{10}}{2^0 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 3^2}$$

$$2364 := \frac{2^4 + 3^5 + 6^0 + 4^9}{2^1 + 3^2 + 6^2 + 4^3}$$

$$2364 := \frac{2^4 + 3^5 + 6^0 + 4^9}{2^1 + 3^2 + 6^2 + 4^3}$$

$$2365 := \frac{2^{15} + 3^0 + 6^3 + 5^3}{2^1 + 3^0 + 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2365 := \frac{2^{15} + 3^0 + 6^3 + 5^3}{2^1 + 3^0 + 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2366 := \frac{2^6 + 3^{10} + 6^0 + 6^2}{2^2 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 6^1}$$

$$2366 := \frac{2^6 + 3^{10} + 6^0 + 6^2}{2^2 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 6^1}$$

$$2367 := \frac{2^7 + 3^{11} + 6^3 + 7^4}{2^5 + 3^0 + 6^2 + 7^1}$$

$$2367 := \frac{2^7 + 3^{11} + 6^3 + 7^4}{2^5 + 3^0 + 6^2 + 7^1}$$

$$2368 := \frac{2^5 + 3^8 - 6^0 + 8^3}{-2^0 - 3^0 + 6^1 - 8^0}$$

$$2369 := \frac{2^9 + 3^7 + 6^3 + 9^4}{2^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2369 := \frac{2^9 + 3^7 + 6^3 + 9^4}{2^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2370 := \frac{2^7 + 3^9 + 7^6 + 0^1}{2^3 + 3^0 + 7^2 + 0^1}$$

$$2370 := \frac{2^7 + 3^9 + 7^6 + 0^1}{2^3 + 3^0 + 7^2 + 0^1}$$

$$2371 := \frac{-2^1 - 3^3 + 7^4 - 1^0}{-2^1 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2371 := \frac{2^5 - 3^5 + 7^5 + 1^5}{-2^1 + 3^1 + 7^1 - 1^1}$$

$$2372 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^5 + 7^4 + 2^{13}}{2^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2373 := \frac{2^5 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 3^{10}}{2^3 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 3^2}$$

$$2374 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^8 + 7^5 + 4^6}{2^0 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 4^0}$$

$$2374 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^8 + 7^5 + 4^6}{2^0 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 4^0}$$

$$2375 := \frac{2^0 + 3^7 + 7^5 + 5^1}{2^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2375 := \frac{2^0 + 3^7 + 7^5 + 5^1}{2^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2376 := \frac{2^{13} + 3^2 + 7^1 + 6^4}{2^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2377 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^9 + 7^3 + 7^3}{2^2 + 3^1 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2377 := \frac{2^{10} + 3^9 + 7^3 + 7^3}{2^2 + 3^1 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2378 := \frac{2^8 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 8^4}{2^2 + 3^1 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2378 := \frac{2^8 + 3^5 + 7^5 + 8^4}{2^2 + 3^1 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2379 := \frac{2^{15} + 3^7 + 7^0 + 9^3}{2^1 + 3^1 + 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2379 := \frac{2^{15} + 3^7 + 7^0 + 9^3}{2^1 + 3^1 + 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2380 := \frac{2^7 + 3^7 + 8^2 + 0^0}{-2^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2381 := \frac{-2^6 + 3^6 + 8^4 + 1^0}{-2^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2382 := \frac{2^2 + 3^{10} + 8^0 + 2^{20}}{2^6 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 2^8}$$

$$2382 := \frac{2^2 + 3^{10} + 8^0 + 2^{20}}{2^6 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 2^8}$$

$$2383 := \frac{2^9 + 3^0 + 8^5 + 3^4}{2^0 + 3^1 + 8^0 + 3^2}$$

$$2383 := \frac{2^9 + 3^0 + 8^5 + 3^4}{2^0 + 3^1 + 8^0 + 3^2}$$

$$2384 := \frac{2^{11} + 3^4 - 8^0 + 4^4}{-2^0 - 3^0 - 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2385 := \frac{2^{16} + 3^9 + 8^4 + 5^6}{2^1 + 3^2 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$2385 := \frac{2^{16} + 3^9 + 8^4 + 5^6}{2^1 + 3^2 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$2386 := \frac{2^{19} + 3^9 + 8^0 + 6^2}{2^0 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 6^3}$$

$$2386 := \frac{2^{19} + 3^9 + 8^0 + 6^2}{2^0 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 6^3}$$

$$2387 := \frac{2^6 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 7^3}{2^1 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2387 := \frac{2^6 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 7^3}{2^1 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2388 := \frac{2^{20} + 3^{11} + 8^0 + 8^4}{2^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 8^3}$$

$$2388 := \frac{2^{20} + 3^{11} + 8^0 + 8^4}{2^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 8^3}$$

$$2389 := \frac{2^{13} + 3^9 + 8^2 + 9^3}{2^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2389 := \frac{2^{13} + 3^9 + 8^2 + 9^3}{2^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2390 := \frac{2^{18} + 3^3 + 9^3 + 0^1}{2^0 + 3^3 + 9^2 + 0^0}$$

$$2390 := \frac{2^{18} + 3^3 + 9^3 + 0^1}{2^0 + 3^3 + 9^2 + 0^0}$$

$$2391 := \frac{2^9 + 3^{11} + 9^5 + 1^0}{2^3 + 3^2 + 9^2 + 1^0}$$

$$2391 := \frac{2^9 + 3^{11} + 9^5 + 1^0}{2^3 + 3^2 + 9^2 + 1^0}$$

$$2392 := \frac{2^2 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 2^6}{2^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 2^3}$$

$$2392 := \frac{2^2 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 2^6}{2^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 2^3}$$

$$2393 := \frac{2^{13} + 3^9 + 9^5 + 3^{10}}{2^4 + 3^2 + 9^1 + 3^3}$$

$$2393 := \frac{2^{13} + 3^9 + 9^5 + 3^{10}}{2^4 + 3^2 + 9^1 + 3^3}$$

$$2394 := \frac{2^{15} + 3^1 + 9^3 + 4^2}{2^0 + 3^1 + 9^1 + 4^0}$$

$$2394 := \frac{2^{15} + 3^1 + 9^3 + 4^2}{2^0 + 3^1 + 9^1 + 4^0}$$

$$2395 := \frac{2^{17} + 3^3 + 9^0 + 5^4}{2^1 + 3^3 + 9^0 + 5^2}$$

$$2396 := \frac{2^{12} + 3^3 + 9^2 + 6^5}{2^1 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2397 := \frac{2^{17} + 3^3 + 9^3 + 7^1}{2^1 + 3^1 + 9^0 + 7^2}$$

$$2398 := \frac{2^{19} + 3^4 + 9^3 + 8^2}{2^7 + 3^2 + 9^2 + 8^0}$$

$$2398 := \frac{2^{19} + 3^4 + 9^3 + 8^2}{2^7 + 3^2 + 9^2 + 8^0}$$

$$2399 := \frac{2^6 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 9^4}{2^3 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2399 := \frac{2^6 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 9^4}{2^3 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2403 := \frac{2^0 + 4^5 + 0^0 + 3^{10}}{2^3 + 4^2 + 0^1 + 3^0}$$

$$2403 := \frac{2^0 + 4^5 + 0^0 + 3^{10}}{2^3 + 4^2 + 0^1 + 3^0}$$

$$2405 := \frac{2^{12} + 4^7 + 0^1 + 5^7}{2^5 + 4^1 + 0^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2405 := \frac{2^{12} + 4^7 + 0^1 + 5^7}{2^5 + 4^1 + 0^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2406 := \frac{2^{19} + 4^1 + 0^1 + 6^3}{2^0 + 4^0 + 0^1 + 6^3}$$

$$2406 := \frac{2^{19} + 4^1 + 0^1 + 6^3}{2^0 + 4^0 + 0^1 + 6^3}$$

$$2407 := \frac{2^0 + 4^1 + 0^0 + 7^4}{-2^0 + 4^0 + 0^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2408 := \frac{-2^3 + 4^8 + 0^1 - 8^3}{2^1 + 4^2 + 0^0 + 8^1}$$

$$2409 := \frac{-2^3 + 4^6 + 0^0 + 9^3}{-2^0 + 4^0 + 0^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2413 := \frac{2^1 + 4^6 - 1^0 + 3^6}{-2^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2414 := \frac{2^9 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 4^7}{2^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2414 := \frac{2^9 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 4^7}{2^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2415 := \frac{2^{15} + 4^8 + 1^0 + 5^5}{2^5 + 4^1 + 1^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2415 := \frac{2^{15} + 4^8 + 1^0 + 5^5}{2^5 + 4^1 + 1^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2416 := \frac{-2^0 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 6^5}{2^1 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2417 := \frac{-2^0 + 4^2 + 1^0 + 7^4}{-2^0 + 4^1 - 1^0 - 7^0}$$

$$2419 := \frac{2^5 - 4^5 - 1^0 + 9^5}{-2^1 + 4^2 + 1^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2422 := \frac{-2^1 - 4^4 - 2^{10} + 2^{15}}{2^0 + 4^1 + 2^2 + 2^2}$$

$$2423 := \frac{2^6 + 4^7 + 2^9 + 3^0}{2^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2423 := \frac{2^6 + 4^7 + 2^9 + 3^0}{2^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2424 := \frac{2^3 + 4^3 + 2^9 + 4^7}{2^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2424 := \frac{2^3 + 4^3 + 2^9 + 4^7}{2^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2425 := \frac{2^{10} + 4^7 + 2^{13} + 5^6}{2^2 + 4^1 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$2425 := \frac{2^{10} + 4^7 + 2^{13} + 5^6}{2^2 + 4^1 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$2426 := \frac{2^1 + 4^4 + 2^{12} + 6^5}{2^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2426 := \frac{2^1 + 4^4 + 2^{12} + 6^5}{2^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2427 := \frac{2^3 + 4^1 + 2^{17} + 7^4}{2^0 + 4^0 + 2^2 + 7^2}$$

$$2428 := \frac{2^2 + 4^2 + 2^{15} + 8^5}{2^0 + 4^2 + 2^1 + 8^1}$$

$$2428 := \frac{2^2 + 4^2 + 2^{15} + 8^5}{2^0 + 4^2 + 2^1 + 8^1}$$

$$2429 := \frac{2^0 + 4^6 + 2^3 + 9^5}{2^0 + 4^2 + 2^3 + 9^0}$$

$$2429 := \frac{2^0 + 4^6 + 2^3 + 9^5}{2^0 + 4^2 + 2^3 + 9^0}$$

$$2430 := \frac{2^6 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 0^0}{2^0 + 4^2 + 3^2 + 0^0}$$

$$2430 := \frac{2^6 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 0^0}{2^0 + 4^2 + 3^2 + 0^0}$$

$$2431 := \frac{2^{15} + 4^5 + 3^5 - 1^0}{2^3 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2432 := \frac{2^0 + 4^1 + 3^{11} + 2^{20}}{2^0 + 4^1 + 3^5 + 2^8}$$

$$2432 := \frac{2^0 + 4^1 + 3^{11} + 2^{20}}{2^0 + 4^1 + 3^5 + 2^8}$$

$$2433 := \frac{2^{15} + 4^5 + 3^3 + 3^5}{2^0 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 3^2}$$

$$2434 := \frac{-2^3 - 4^0 + 3^7 + 4^4}{-2^0 - 4^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2435 := \frac{2^{15} + 4^3 + 3^5 + 5^6}{2^1 + 4^1 + 3^2 + 5^1}$$

$$2435 := \frac{2^{15} + 4^3 + 3^5 + 5^6}{2^1 + 4^1 + 3^2 + 5^1}$$

$$2436 := \frac{2^{17} + 4^0 + 3^1 + 6^5}{2^1 + 4^2 + 3^1 + 6^2}$$

$$2437 := \frac{2^3 + 4^0 + 3^5 + 7^5}{2^0 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2438 := \frac{-2^2 + 4^4 + 3^7 - 8^0}{2^0 + 4^0 - 3^2 + 8^1}$$

$$2439 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^5 + 3^3 + 9^5}{2^1 + 4^2 + 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2439 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^5 + 3^3 + 9^5}{2^1 + 4^2 + 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2440 := \frac{-2^{15} - 4^2 + 4^9 + 0^1}{2^5 - 4^0 + 4^3 - 0^0}$$

$$2442 := \frac{2^0 + 4^0 - 4^5 + 2^{15}}{2^0 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 2^2}$$

$$2443 := \frac{2^8 + 4^5 + 4^5 + 3^9}{2^0 + 4^0 + 4^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2444 := \frac{-2^2 - 4^3 - 4^6 + 4^7}{2^1 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2445 := \frac{2^9 + 4^5 + 4^5 + 5^7}{2^3 + 4^1 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$2445 := \frac{2^9 + 4^5 + 4^5 + 5^7}{2^3 + 4^1 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$2446 := \frac{2^2 + 4^3 + 4^8 + 6^5}{2^2 + 4^1 + 4^2 + 6^1}$$

$$2446 := \frac{2^2 + 4^3 + 4^8 + 6^5}{2^2 + 4^1 + 4^2 + 6^1}$$

$$2447 := \frac{2^1 + 4^3 + 4^4 + 7^5}{2^0 + 4^0 + 4^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2447 := \frac{2^1 + 4^3 + 4^4 + 7^5}{2^0 + 4^0 + 4^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2448 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^3 + 4^5 + 8^3}{2^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2448 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^3 + 4^5 + 8^3}{2^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2449 := \frac{2^7 + 4^5 + 4^5 + 9^5}{2^2 + 4^1 + 4^2 + 9^0}$$

$$2449 := \frac{2^7 + 4^5 + 4^5 + 9^5}{2^2 + 4^1 + 4^2 + 9^0}$$

$$2450 := \frac{2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 0^0}{2^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2450 := \frac{2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 0^0}{2^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2451 := \frac{-2^5 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 1^0}{2^0 + 4^0 + 5^2 + 1^0}$$

$$2452 := \frac{-2^0 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 2^{16}}{2^0 + 4^0 + 5^2 + 2^0}$$

$$2453 := \frac{2^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 3^{10}}{2^1 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2453 := \frac{2^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 3^{10}}{2^1 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2454 := \frac{-2^{13} - 4^0 - 5^6 + 4^8}{2^2 + 4^1 + 5^1 + 4^1}$$

$$2455 := \frac{2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 5^8}{2^5 + 4^1 + 5^1 + 5^3}$$

$$2455 := \frac{2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 5^8}{2^5 + 4^1 + 5^1 + 5^3}$$

$$2456 := \frac{2^1 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 6^6}{2^0 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2456 := \frac{2^1 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 6^6}{2^0 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2457 := \frac{2^7 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 7^1}{2^0 + 4^0 + 5^2 + 7^0}$$

$$2457 := \frac{2^7 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 7^1}{2^0 + 4^0 + 5^2 + 7^0}$$

$$2458 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^0 + 5^0 + 8^4}{2^1 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2458 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^0 + 5^0 + 8^4}{2^1 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2459 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^7 + 5^1 + 9^1}{2^2 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2459 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^7 + 5^1 + 9^1}{2^2 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2460 := \frac{2^{11} + 4^2 + 6^5 + 0^1}{2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 0^0}$$

$$2460 := \frac{2^{11} + 4^2 + 6^5 + 0^1}{2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 0^0}$$

$$2461 := \frac{2^{13} - 4^5 + 6^3 - 1^0}{-2^0 - 4^0 + 6^1 - 1^0}$$

$$2462 := \frac{2^3 + 4^2 + 6^5 + 2^{11}}{2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$2462 := \frac{2^3 + 4^2 + 6^5 + 2^{11}}{2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$2463 := \frac{2^{11} + 4^0 + 6^5 + 3^3}{2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2463 := \frac{2^{11} + 4^0 + 6^5 + 3^3}{2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2464 := \frac{2^5 + 4^5 + 6^5 + 4^5}{2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2464 := \frac{2^5 + 4^5 + 6^5 + 4^5}{2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2465 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^6 + 6^2 + 5^0}{2^1 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$2465 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^6 + 6^2 + 5^0}{2^1 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$2466 := \frac{2^{11} + 4^1 + 6^2 + 6^5}{2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2466 := \frac{2^{11} + 4^1 + 6^2 + 6^5}{2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2467 := \frac{2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^5}{2^0 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2468 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^2 + 6^2 + 8^4}{2^1 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2468 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^2 + 6^2 + 8^4}{2^1 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2468 := \frac{-2^5 - 4^5 + 6^5 + 8^5}{-2^1 + 4^1 + 6^1 + 8^1}$$

$$2469 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^2 + 6^7 + 9^3}{2^3 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 9^1}$$

$$2469 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^2 + 6^7 + 9^3}{2^3 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 9^1}$$

$$2470 := \frac{2^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 0^0}{-2^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2471 := \frac{-2^6 + 4^5 + 7^6 - 1^0}{-2^0 - 4^0 + 7^2 + 1^0}$$

$$2472 := \frac{2^{11} + 4^0 + 7^7 + 2^{17}}{2^1 + 4^4 + 7^0 + 2^7}$$

$$2472 := \frac{2^{11} + 4^0 + 7^7 + 2^{17}}{2^1 + 4^4 + 7^0 + 2^7}$$

$$2473 := \frac{2^2 + 4^5 + 7^6 + 3^3}{2^2 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 3^3}$$

$$2473 := \frac{2^2 + 4^5 + 7^6 + 3^3}{2^2 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 3^3}$$

$$2474 := \frac{2^0 + 4^8 + 7^2 + 4^8}{2^1 + 4^0 + 7^2 + 4^0}$$

$$2475 := \frac{2^9 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 5^1}{2^0 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$2475 := \frac{2^9 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 5^1}{2^0 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$2476 := \frac{2^{17} + 4^0 + 7^1 + 6^7}{2^7 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 6^2}$$

$$2476 := \frac{2^{17} + 4^0 + 7^1 + 6^7}{2^7 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 6^2}$$

$$2477 := \frac{2^{10} + 4^7 + 7^1 + 7^4}{2^1 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2477 := \frac{2^{10} + 4^7 + 7^1 + 7^4}{2^1 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2478 := \frac{2^0 - 4^2 + 7^5 + 8^5}{2^0 + 4^1 + 7^1 + 8^1}$$

$$2479 := \frac{2^{15} + 4^1 + 7^5 + 9^0}{2^1 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2479 := \frac{2^{15} + 4^1 + 7^5 + 9^0}{2^1 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2480 := \frac{-2^9 - 4^2 + 8^5 + 0^1}{2^0 + 4^1 + 8^1 + 0^1}$$

$$2481 := \frac{-2^9 - 4^1 + 8^5 + 1^0}{-2^0 + 4^2 - 8^0 - 1^0}$$

$$2482 := \frac{-2^2 - 4^3 + 8^5 + 2^{11}}{2^0 + 4^0 + 8^1 + 2^2}$$

$$2483 := \frac{2^{11} + 4^7 + 8^4 + 3^9}{2^1 + 4^1 + 8^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2484 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^4 + 8^1 + 4^7}{2^0 + 4^1 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2484 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^4 + 8^1 + 4^7}{2^0 + 4^1 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2485 := \frac{2^{16} + 4^8 + 8^1 + 5^4}{2^2 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$2485 := \frac{2^{16} + 4^8 + 8^1 + 5^4}{2^2 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$2486 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^5 + 8^3 + 6^3}{2^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2486 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^5 + 8^3 + 6^3}{2^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2487 := \frac{2^9 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 7^0}{2^0 + 4^1 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2487 := \frac{2^9 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 7^0}{2^0 + 4^1 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2488 := \frac{2^3 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 8^3}{2^0 + 4^1 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2488 := \frac{2^3 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 8^3}{2^0 + 4^1 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2489 := \frac{2^1 + 4^6 + 8^6 + 9^2}{2^1 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^2}$$

$$2489 := \frac{2^1 + 4^6 + 8^6 + 9^2}{2^1 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^2}$$

$$2490 := \frac{2^4 + 4^9 + 9^5 + 0^0}{2^5 + 4^2 + 9^2 + 0^1}$$

$$2490 := \frac{2^4 + 4^9 + 9^5 + 0^0}{2^5 + 4^2 + 9^2 + 0^1}$$

$$2492 := \frac{-2^0 - 4^6 + 9^5 - 2^7}{2^0 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 2^4}$$

$$2493 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^5 + 9^3 + 3^3}{2^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2493 := \frac{2^{13} + 4^5 + 9^3 + 3^3}{2^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2494 := \frac{-2^0 - 4^7 + 9^3 + 4^8}{2^1 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 4^2}$$

$$2495 := \frac{2^7 + 4^2 + 9^4 + 5^7}{2^2 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 5^2}$$

$$2495 := \frac{2^7 + 4^2 + 9^4 + 5^7}{2^2 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 5^2}$$

$$2496 := \frac{2^5 - 4^6 + 9^4 - 6^0}{-2^0 - 4^0 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$2497 := \frac{2^1 + 4^5 + 9^4 + 7^4}{2^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2497 := \frac{2^1 + 4^5 + 9^4 + 7^4}{2^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2498 := \frac{2^0 + 4^3 + 9^2 + 8^6}{2^4 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^2}$$

$$2498 := \frac{2^0 + 4^3 + 9^2 + 8^6}{2^4 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 8^2}$$

$$2499 := \frac{-2^{12} + 4^7 - 9^3 - 9^4}{-2^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2502 := \frac{2^1 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 2^{18}}{2^1 + 5^1 + 0^0 + 2^7}$$

$$2502 := \frac{2^1 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 2^{18}}{2^1 + 5^1 + 0^0 + 2^7}$$

$$2503 := \frac{2^{10} - 5^0 + 0^1 + 3^{10}}{2^4 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2504 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^2 - 0^0 + 4^8}{2^0 + 5^2 + 0^1 + 4^0}$$

$$2505 := \frac{2^2 - 5^4 + 0^0 + 5^5}{-2^0 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2506 := \frac{-2^8 - 5^0 - 0^0 + 6^5}{2^0 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2507 := \frac{-2^9 + 5^5 + 0^1 + 7^4}{-2^0 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2508 := \frac{-2^6 + 5^6 - 0^0 - 8^3}{2^2 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 8^0}$$

$$2509 := \frac{2^{18} + 5^6 + 0^0 + 9^3}{2^2 + 5^2 + 0^0 + 9^2}$$

$$2509 := \frac{2^{18} + 5^6 + 0^0 + 9^3}{2^2 + 5^2 + 0^0 + 9^2}$$

$$2511 := \frac{2^{15} - 5^3 - 1^0 + 1^0}{2^3 + 5^1 - 1^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2512 := \frac{-2^5 - 5^4 + 1^0 + 2^{13}}{-2^0 + 5^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2513 := \frac{2^{16} + 5^7 + 1^0 + 3^9}{2^5 + 5^1 + 1^0 + 3^3}$$

$$2513 := \frac{2^{16} + 5^7 + 1^0 + 3^9}{2^5 + 5^1 + 1^0 + 3^3}$$

$$2514 := \frac{2^6 + 5^7 + 1^0 - 4^4}{2^0 + 5^2 + 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2515 := \frac{2^{14} + 5^5 + 1^0 + 5^5}{2^1 + 5^0 + 1^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2515 := \frac{2^{14} + 5^5 + 1^0 + 5^5}{2^1 + 5^0 + 1^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2516 := \frac{2^{13} - 5^5 + 1^0 - 6^2}{-2^0 + 5^0 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2517 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^3 + 1^0 + 7^3}{-2^1 + 5^0 + 1^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2517 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^3 + 1^0 + 7^3}{-2^1 + 5^0 + 1^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2518 := \frac{2^{13} - 5^3 - 1^0 - 8^3}{-2^0 - 5^1 + 1^0 + 8^1}$$

$$2519 := \frac{2^{13} - 5^4 - 1^0 - 9^1}{2^1 - 5^0 + 1^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2520 := \frac{-2^3 - 5^4 + 2^{13} + 0^0}{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2521 := \frac{2^2 + 5^1 + 2^{16} + 1^0}{2^2 + 5^1 + 2^4 + 1^0}$$

$$2521 := \frac{2^2 + 5^1 + 2^{16} + 1^0}{2^2 + 5^1 + 2^4 + 1^0}$$

$$2522 := \frac{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^4 + 2^{15}}{2^1 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 2^3}$$

$$2522 := \frac{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^4 + 2^{15}}{2^1 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 2^3}$$

$$2523 := \frac{2^8 + 5^0 + 2^{14} + 3^{10}}{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 3^3}$$

$$2523 := \frac{2^8 + 5^0 + 2^{14} + 3^{10}}{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 3^3}$$

$$2524 := \frac{2^0 - 5^4 + 2^{13} + 4^1}{-2^0 - 5^0 + 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2525 := \frac{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^{11} + 5^6}{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^2 + 5^0}$$

$$2525 := \frac{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^{11} + 5^6}{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^2 + 5^0}$$

$$2526 := \frac{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^{14} + 6^4}{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^2 + 6^0}$$

$$2526 := \frac{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^{14} + 6^4}{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^2 + 6^0}$$

$$2527 := \frac{2^0 + 5^4 + 2^8 + 7^5}{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$2527 := \frac{2^0 + 5^4 + 2^8 + 7^5}{2^0 + 5^0 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$2528 := \frac{2^4 - 5^4 + 2^{13} + 8^0}{-2^0 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$2529 := \frac{2^{12} + 5^6 + 2^{16} + 9^3}{2^2 + 5^1 + 2^4 + 9^1}$$

$$2529 := \frac{2^{12} + 5^6 + 2^{16} + 9^3}{2^2 + 5^1 + 2^4 + 9^1}$$

$$2530 := \frac{2^{10} + 5^1 + 3^8 + 0^1}{2^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2530 := \frac{2^{10} + 5^1 + 3^8 + 0^1}{2^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2531 := \frac{2^{15} + 5^3 + 3^2 + 1^0}{2^1 + 5^0 + 3^2 + 1^0}$$

$$2531 := \frac{2^{15} + 5^3 + 3^2 + 1^0}{2^1 + 5^0 + 3^2 + 1^0}$$

$$2532 := \frac{2^7 + 5^5 + 3^9 + 2^{15}}{2^1 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 2^4}$$

$$2533 := \frac{2^{15} + 5^3 + 3^2 + 3^3}{2^1 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2533 := \frac{2^{15} + 5^3 + 3^2 + 3^3}{2^1 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2534 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^6 + 3^0 + 4^3}{2^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2534 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^6 + 3^0 + 4^3}{2^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$2535 := \frac{2^1 + 5^1 + 3^9 + 5^5}{2^1 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 5^1}$	$2546 := \frac{2^1 + 5^{10} + 4^0 + 6^6}{2^9 + 5^5 + 4^0 + 6^3}$	$2557 := \frac{2^{14} + 5^2 + 5^2 + 7^5}{2^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 7^0}$
$2535 := \frac{2^1 + 5^1 + 3^9 + 5^5}{2^1 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 5^1}$	$2546 := \frac{2^1 + 5^{10} + 4^0 + 6^6}{2^9 + 5^5 + 4^0 + 6^3}$	$2557 := \frac{2^{14} + 5^2 + 5^2 + 7^5}{2^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 7^0}$
$2536 := \frac{2^{15} + 5^1 + 3^3 + 6^5}{2^1 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 6^1}$	$2547 := \frac{2^9 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 7^2}{2^1 + 5^0 + 4^2 + 7^1}$	$2558 := \frac{2^{11} - 5^0 - 5^0 + 8^3}{-2^0 - 5^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$
$2537 := \frac{2^{13} + 5^2 + 3^9 + 7^1}{2^1 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 7^1}$	$2547 := \frac{2^9 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 7^2}{2^1 + 5^0 + 4^2 + 7^1}$	$2559 := \frac{-2^4 + 5^5 + 5^5 + 9^4}{2^1 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$
$2538 := \frac{2^5 + 5^7 + 3^2 + 8^3}{2^1 + 5^0 + 3^3 + 8^0}$	$2548 := \frac{-2^0 + 5^5 - 4^3 - 8^3}{-2^0 - 5^0 + 4^1 - 8^0}$	$2560 := \frac{2^3 - 5^6 + 6^8 + 0^0}{2^5 + 5^4 - 6^1 - 0^0}$
$2538 := \frac{2^5 + 5^7 + 3^2 + 8^3}{2^1 + 5^0 + 3^3 + 8^0}$	$2549 := \frac{2^2 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 9^3}{2^2 + 5^1 + 4^2 + 9^0}$	$2561 := \frac{2^1 + 5^7 - 6^4 - 1^0}{-2^1 - 5^1 + 6^2 + 1^0}$
$2539 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^3}{2^1 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 9^1}$	$2549 := \frac{2^2 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 9^3}{2^2 + 5^1 + 4^2 + 9^0}$	$2562 := \frac{2^0 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 2^{14}}{2^0 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 2^0}$
$2539 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^3}{2^1 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 9^1}$	$2551 := \frac{2^8 - 5^5 + 5^6 - 1^0}{2^1 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 1^0}$	$2562 := \frac{2^0 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 2^{14}}{2^0 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 2^0}$
$2540 := \frac{-2^7 + 5^6 - 4^4 - 0^0}{2^0 + 5^0 + 4^1 + 0^1}$	$2552 := \frac{2^1 + 5^3 + 5^8 + 2^{20}}{2^1 + 5^2 + 5^2 + 2^9}$	$2563 := \frac{2^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^7}{2^1 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$
$2541 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^7 + 4^7 + 1^0}{2^3 + 5^2 + 4^1 + 1^0}$	$2552 := \frac{2^1 + 5^3 + 5^8 + 2^{20}}{2^1 + 5^2 + 5^2 + 2^9}$	$2563 := \frac{2^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 3^7}{2^1 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$
$2541 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^7 + 4^7 + 1^0}{2^3 + 5^2 + 4^1 + 1^0}$	$2553 := \frac{2^{14} + 5^8 + 5^8 + 3^8}{2^6 + 5^3 + 5^3 + 3^0}$	$2564 := \frac{2^4 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 4^4}{-2^0 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 4^0}$
$2542 := \frac{2^0 + 5^{11} + 4^5 + 2^7}{2^9 + 5^6 + 4^5 + 2^{11}}$	$2553 := \frac{2^{14} + 5^8 + 5^8 + 3^8}{2^6 + 5^3 + 5^3 + 3^0}$	$2565 := \frac{2^{14} + 5^8 + 6^5 + 5^8}{2^7 + 5^2 + 6^2 + 5^3}$
$2542 := \frac{2^0 + 5^{11} + 4^5 + 2^7}{2^9 + 5^6 + 4^5 + 2^{11}}$	$2554 := \frac{2^3 + 5^3 + 5^8 + 4^1}{2^1 + 5^2 + 5^3 + 4^0}$	$2565 := \frac{2^{14} + 5^8 + 6^5 + 5^8}{2^7 + 5^2 + 6^2 + 5^3}$
$2543 := \frac{2^5 + 5^4 + 4^1 + 3^9}{2^0 + 5^1 + 4^0 + 3^0}$	$2554 := \frac{2^3 + 5^3 + 5^8 + 4^1}{2^1 + 5^2 + 5^3 + 4^0}$	$2566 := \frac{-2^0 - 5^2 + 6^4 + 6^4}{-2^0 - 5^1 + 6^0 + 6^1}$
$2543 := \frac{2^5 + 5^4 + 4^1 + 3^9}{2^0 + 5^1 + 4^0 + 3^0}$	$2555 := \frac{2^{14} + 5^0 + 5^2 + 5^7}{2^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 5^2}$	$2567 := \frac{2^{17} + 5^1 + 6^1 + 7^4}{2^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 7^2}$
$2544 := \frac{2^{13} - 5^4 + 4^0 + 4^3}{-2^0 - 5^0 + 4^0 + 4^1}$	$2555 := \frac{2^{14} + 5^0 + 5^2 + 5^7}{2^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 5^2}$	$2567 := \frac{2^{17} + 5^1 + 6^1 + 7^4}{2^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 7^2}$
$2545 := \frac{2^2 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 5^4}{2^2 + 5^0 + 4^2 + 5^1}$	$2556 := \frac{2^{16} + 5^4 + 5^6 + 6^1}{2^0 + 5^1 + 5^2 + 6^0}$	$2568 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^5 - 6^2 - 8^0}{-2^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$
$2545 := \frac{2^2 + 5^1 + 4^8 + 5^4}{2^2 + 5^0 + 4^2 + 5^1}$	$2556 := \frac{2^{16} + 5^4 + 5^6 + 6^1}{2^0 + 5^1 + 5^2 + 6^0}$	$2569 := \frac{2^0 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 9^5}{2^3 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 9^1}$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 2569 := \frac{2^0 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 9^5}{2^3 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 9^1} & 2580 := \frac{-2^5 + 5^5 - 8^3 - 0^0}{-2^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 0^1} & 2592 := \frac{2^1 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^5}{2^1 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 2^4} \\
 2570 := \frac{2^{19} + 5^8 + 7^1 + 0^1}{2^3 + 5^1 + 7^3 + 0^1} & 2581 := \frac{2^{20} - 5^4 - 8^2 - 1^0}{2^{10} - 5^4 + 8^1 - 1^0} & 2593 := \frac{2^{19} + 5^8 + 9^7 + 3^9}{2^2 + 5^1 + 9^1 + 3^7} \\
 2570 := \frac{2^{19} + 5^8 + 7^1 + 0^1}{2^3 + 5^1 + 7^3 + 0^1} & 2582 := \frac{2^{10} + 5^7 + 8^0 + 2^{14}}{2^1 + 5^2 + 8^1 + 2^1} & 2593 := \frac{2^{19} + 5^8 + 9^7 + 3^9}{2^2 + 5^1 + 9^1 + 3^7} \\
 2571 := \frac{-2^{14} - 5^7 + 7^6 - 1^0}{2^1 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 1^0} & 2582 := \frac{2^{10} + 5^7 + 8^0 + 2^{14}}{2^1 + 5^2 + 8^1 + 2^1} & 2594 := \frac{2^{15} + 5^3 + 9^1 + 4^7}{2^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 4^2} \\
 2572 := \frac{2^9 + 5^6 + 7^3 + 2^{12}}{2^0 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 2^0} & 2583 := \frac{2^{13} + 5^3 + 8^5 + 3^5}{2^0 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 3^2} & 2594 := \frac{2^{15} + 5^3 + 9^1 + 4^7}{2^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 4^2} \\
 2572 := \frac{2^9 + 5^6 + 7^3 + 2^{12}}{2^0 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 2^0} & 2583 := \frac{2^{13} + 5^3 + 8^5 + 3^5}{2^0 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 3^2} & 2595 := \frac{-2^{12} + 5^1 + 9^4 + 5^3}{-2^1 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 5^0} \\
 2573 := \frac{2^2 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 3^{10}}{2^1 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 3^2} & 2584 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^2 + 8^3 - 4^0}{-2^0 - 5^0 - 8^0 + 4^1} & 2596 := \frac{2^{15} + 5^7 + 9^3 + 6^1}{2^0 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 6^2} \\
 2573 := \frac{2^2 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 3^{10}}{2^1 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 3^2} & 2585 := \frac{2^{15} + 5^1 + 8^7 + 5^6}{2^4 + 5^3 + 8^2 + 5^4} & 2596 := \frac{2^{15} + 5^7 + 9^3 + 6^1}{2^0 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 6^2} \\
 2574 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^5 + 7^5 + 4^8}{2^0 + 5^2 + 7^1 + 4^0} & 2585 := \frac{2^{15} + 5^1 + 8^7 + 5^6}{2^4 + 5^3 + 8^2 + 5^4} & 2597 := \frac{2^2 + 5^0 + 9^4 + 7^5}{2^1 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 7^0} \\
 2575 := \frac{2^0 + 5^4 + 7^6 + 5^6}{2^0 + 5^0 + 7^2 + 5^0} & 2586 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^2 + 8^3 + 6^0}{-2^0 - 5^1 + 8^0 + 6^1} & 2597 := \frac{2^2 + 5^0 + 9^4 + 7^5}{2^1 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 7^0} \\
 2575 := \frac{2^0 + 5^4 + 7^6 + 5^6}{2^0 + 5^0 + 7^2 + 5^0} & 2587 := \frac{2^{10} + 5^2 + 8^5 + 7^4}{2^0 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 7^1} & 2598 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^6 + 9^0 + 8^3}{2^2 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 8^0} \\
 2576 := \frac{2^1 + 5^3 + 7^4 + 6^5}{2^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 6^0} & 2587 := \frac{2^{10} + 5^2 + 8^5 + 7^4}{2^0 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 7^1} & 2598 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^6 + 9^0 + 8^3}{2^2 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 8^0} \\
 2576 := \frac{2^1 + 5^3 + 7^4 + 6^5}{2^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 6^0} & 2588 := \frac{-2^5 + 5^6 - 8^0 - 8^2}{-2^0 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 8^0} & 2599 := \frac{-2^{12} + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^4}{-2^1 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 9^0} \\
 2577 := \frac{2^1 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 7^6}{2^3 + 5^2 + 7^1 + 7^1} & 2589 := \frac{2^{13} + 5^7 + 8^5 + 9^1}{2^2 + 5^2 + 8^1 + 9^1} & 2602 := \frac{-2^0 + 6^5 - 0^0 + 2^5}{2^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 2^0} \\
 2578 := \frac{2^{20} + 5^6 + 7^0 + 8^3}{2^0 + 5^1 + 7^3 + 8^2} & 2589 := \frac{2^{13} + 5^7 + 8^5 + 9^1}{2^2 + 5^2 + 8^1 + 9^1} & 2603 := \frac{2^5 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 3^0}{2^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 3^0} \\
 2578 := \frac{2^{20} + 5^6 + 7^0 + 8^3}{2^0 + 5^1 + 7^3 + 8^2} & 2590 := \frac{-2^{12} + 5^3 + 9^4 + 0^1}{-2^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 0^1} & 2603 := \frac{2^5 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 3^0}{2^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 3^0} \\
 2579 := \frac{2^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^3}{2^2 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 9^0} & 2591 := \frac{2^{11} + 5^4 - 9^2 - 1^0}{-2^1 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 1^0} & 2604 := \frac{2^5 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 4^1}{2^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 4^0} \\
 2579 := \frac{2^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^3}{2^2 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 9^0} & 2592 := \frac{2^1 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^5}{2^1 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 2^4} & 2604 := \frac{2^5 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 4^1}{2^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 4^0}
 \end{array}$$

$2605 := \frac{2^2 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 5^6}{2^2 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 5^0}$	$2623 := \frac{2^0 + 6^4 + 2^2 + 3^9}{2^1 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 3^1}$	$2634 := \frac{2^9 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 4^0}{2^1 + 6^1 + 3^2 + 4^0}$
$2605 := \frac{2^2 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 5^6}{2^2 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 5^0}$	$2623 := \frac{2^0 + 6^4 + 2^2 + 3^9}{2^1 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 3^1}$	$2634 := \frac{2^9 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 4^0}{2^1 + 6^1 + 3^2 + 4^0}$
$2607 := \frac{2^{11} + 6^3 + 0^1 + 7^3}{-2^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 7^0}$	$2624 := \frac{2^5 + 6^5 + 2^{11} + 4^7}{2^0 + 6^0 + 2^2 + 4^1}$	$2635 := \frac{2^{13} + 6^2 + 3^7 + 5^3}{2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$
$2608 := \frac{-2^{11} + 6^5 + 0^1 - 8^3}{-2^0 + 6^0 + 0^0 + 8^0}$	$2624 := \frac{2^5 + 6^5 + 2^{11} + 4^7}{2^0 + 6^0 + 2^2 + 4^1}$	$2635 := \frac{2^{13} + 6^2 + 3^7 + 5^3}{2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$
$2609 := \frac{2^{14} - 6^0 + 0^1 - 9^3}{2^2 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 9^0}$	$2625 := \frac{2^9 + 6^4 + 2^{13} + 5^5}{2^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$	$2636 := \frac{2^8 + 6^0 + 3^{11} + 6^6}{2^2 + 6^2 + 3^2 + 6^2}$
$2610 := \frac{2^{19} - 6^6 - 1^0 - 0^0}{-2^5 + 6^3 - 1^0 + 0^1}$	$2625 := \frac{2^9 + 6^4 + 2^{13} + 5^5}{2^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$	$2636 := \frac{2^8 + 6^0 + 3^{11} + 6^6}{2^2 + 6^2 + 3^2 + 6^2}$
$2613 := \frac{2^{16} + 6^3 - 1^0 + 3^7}{2^4 + 6^1 + 1^0 + 3^1}$	$2626 := \frac{2^6 + 6^2 + 2^9 + 6^6}{2^1 + 6^1 + 2^2 + 6^1}$	$2637 := \frac{2^7 + 6^5 + 3^5 + 7^4}{2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$
$2614 := \frac{2^0 + 6^5 + 1^0 + 4^3}{-2^0 - 6^0 + 1^0 + 4^1}$	$2627 := \frac{2^0 + 6^6 + 2^{14} + 7^1}{2^0 + 6^1 + 2^4 + 7^0}$	$2637 := \frac{2^7 + 6^5 + 3^5 + 7^4}{2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$
$2615 := \frac{2^9 + 6^9 + 1^0 + 5^0}{2^9 + 6^3 + 1^0 + 5^5}$	$2628 := \frac{2^9 + 6^4 + 2^{13} + 8^3}{2^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$	$2638 := \frac{2^9 + 6^0 + 3^{10} + 8^5}{2^0 + 6^1 + 3^3 + 8^0}$
$2615 := \frac{2^9 + 6^9 + 1^0 + 5^0}{2^9 + 6^3 + 1^0 + 5^5}$	$2628 := \frac{2^9 + 6^4 + 2^{13} + 8^3}{2^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$	$2638 := \frac{2^9 + 6^0 + 3^{10} + 8^5}{2^0 + 6^1 + 3^3 + 8^0}$
$2617 := \frac{-2^0 + 6^3 + 1^0 + 7^4}{-2^0 - 6^1 + 1^0 + 7^1}$	$2629 := \frac{2^5 + 6^4 + 2^{15} + 9^2}{2^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 9^1}$	$2639 := \frac{2^9 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 9^4}{2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$
$2618 := \frac{-2^0 + 6^8 + 1^0 - 8^4}{2^7 - 6^0 + 1^0 + 8^3}$	$2629 := \frac{2^5 + 6^4 + 2^{15} + 9^2}{2^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 9^1}$	$2639 := \frac{2^9 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 9^4}{2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$
$2619 := \frac{-2^0 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 9^4}{-2^0 + 6^1 - 1^0 - 9^0}$	$2630 := \frac{2^5 + 6^4 + 3^8 + 0^0}{2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$	$2640 := \frac{2^7 + 6^5 + 4^2 + 0^1}{2^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$
$2620 := \frac{-2^5 - 6^4 + 2^{15} + 0^1}{2^0 + 6^1 + 2^2 + 0^0}$	$2630 := \frac{2^5 + 6^4 + 3^8 + 0^0}{2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$	$2640 := \frac{2^7 + 6^5 + 4^2 + 0^1}{2^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$
$2621 := \frac{2^3 + 6^4 + 2^{15} + 1^0}{2^1 + 6^1 + 2^2 + 1^0}$	$2631 := \frac{-2^1 - 6^4 + 3^8 - 1^0}{-2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 1^0}$	$2641 := \frac{2^{19} + 6^6 + 4^8 + 1^0}{2^3 + 6^3 + 4^2 + 1^0}$
$2621 := \frac{2^3 + 6^4 + 2^{15} + 1^0}{2^1 + 6^1 + 2^2 + 1^0}$	$2632 := \frac{2^0 - 6^4 + 3^8 - 2^1}{-2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$	$2641 := \frac{2^{19} + 6^6 + 4^8 + 1^0}{2^3 + 6^3 + 4^2 + 1^0}$
$2622 := \frac{2^5 + 6^3 + 2^{11} + 2^{13}}{2^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$	$2633 := \frac{2^2 + 6^4 + 3^4 + 3^9}{2^0 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 3^1}$	$2642 := \frac{2^{13} + 6^4 + 4^2 + 2^{15}}{2^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 2^3}$
$2622 := \frac{2^5 + 6^3 + 2^{11} + 2^{13}}{2^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$	$2633 := \frac{2^2 + 6^4 + 3^4 + 3^9}{2^0 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 3^1}$	$2642 := \frac{2^{13} + 6^4 + 4^2 + 2^{15}}{2^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 2^3}$

$2643 := \frac{2^1 + 6^1 + 4^6 + 3^9}{2^0 + 6^0 + 4^1 + 3^1}$	$2653 := \frac{2^8 + 6^2 + 5^6 + 3^0}{2^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 3^1}$	$2663 := \frac{2^{13} + 6^0 + 6^5 + 3^2}{2^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$
$2643 := \frac{2^1 + 6^1 + 4^6 + 3^9}{2^0 + 6^0 + 4^1 + 3^1}$	$2653 := \frac{2^8 + 6^2 + 5^6 + 3^0}{2^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 3^1}$	$2664 := \frac{2^5 + 6^5 + 6^5 + 4^7}{2^0 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 4^1}$
$2644 := \frac{2^{13} + 6^4 + 4^3 + 4^5}{2^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$	$2654 := \frac{2^0 + 6^6 + 5^{11} + 4^{12}}{2^{13} + 6^2 + 5^3 + 4^7}$	$2665 := \frac{2^1 + 6^3 + 6^5 + 5^0}{-2^0 - 6^0 + 6^1 - 5^0}$
$2644 := \frac{2^{13} + 6^4 + 4^3 + 4^5}{2^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$	$2654 := \frac{2^0 + 6^6 + 5^{11} + 4^{12}}{2^{13} + 6^2 + 5^3 + 4^7}$	$2666 := \frac{-2^1 - 6^2 - 6^4 + 6^6}{2^2 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 6^1}$
$2645 := \frac{2^7 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 5^8}{2^3 + 6^2 + 4^1 + 5^3}$	$2655 := \frac{2^{14} + 6^6 + 5^8 + 5^8}{2^5 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 5^3}$	$2667 := \frac{2^5 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 7^0}{2^4 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 7^1}$
$2645 := \frac{2^7 + 6^4 + 4^8 + 5^8}{2^3 + 6^2 + 4^1 + 5^3}$	$2655 := \frac{2^{14} + 6^6 + 5^8 + 5^8}{2^5 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 5^3}$	$2667 := \frac{2^5 + 6^6 + 6^6 + 7^0}{2^4 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 7^1}$
$2646 := \frac{2^{15} + 6^7 + 4^3 + 6^7}{2^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 6^3}$	$2656 := \frac{2^0 + 6^3 - 5^2 + 6^5}{-2^0 - 6^0 - 5^0 + 6^1}$	$2668 := \frac{2^3 + 6^4 + 6^6 + 8^2}{2^3 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 8^1}$
$2646 := \frac{2^{15} + 6^7 + 4^3 + 6^7}{2^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 6^3}$	$2657 := \frac{2^{11} + 6^2 + 5^9 + 7^3}{2^9 + 6^3 + 5^0 + 7^1}$	$2668 := \frac{2^3 + 6^4 + 6^6 + 8^2}{2^3 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 8^1}$
$2647 := \frac{2^{15} + 6^4 + 4^1 + 7^3}{2^0 + 6^0 + 4^1 + 7^1}$	$2657 := \frac{2^{11} + 6^2 + 5^9 + 7^3}{2^9 + 6^3 + 5^0 + 7^1}$	$2669 := \frac{2^{17} + 6^2 + 6^9 + 9^7}{2^{12} + 6^3 + 6^4 + 9^1}$
$2647 := \frac{2^{15} + 6^4 + 4^1 + 7^3}{2^0 + 6^0 + 4^1 + 7^1}$	$2658 := \frac{2^{15} + 6^0 + 5^3 + 8^6}{2^4 + 6^1 + 5^2 + 8^2}$	$2669 := \frac{2^{17} + 6^2 + 6^9 + 9^7}{2^{12} + 6^3 + 6^4 + 9^1}$
$2648 := \frac{2^{11} + 6^5 + 4^4 + 8^3}{2^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$	$2658 := \frac{2^{15} + 6^0 + 5^3 + 8^6}{2^4 + 6^1 + 5^2 + 8^2}$	$2670 := \frac{2^6 + 6^5 + 7^6 + 0^0}{2^2 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 0^1}$
$2648 := \frac{2^{11} + 6^5 + 4^4 + 8^3}{2^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$	$2659 := \frac{2^{12} + 6^7 + 5^8 + 9^3}{2^2 + 6^3 + 5^2 + 9^1}$	$2670 := \frac{2^6 + 6^5 + 7^6 + 0^0}{2^2 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 0^1}$
$2649 := \frac{2^0 + 6^6 + 4^5 + 9^0}{2^1 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 9^1}$	$2659 := \frac{2^{12} + 6^7 + 5^8 + 9^3}{2^2 + 6^3 + 5^2 + 9^1}$	$2671 := \frac{-2^5 + 6^5 - 7^4 - 1^0}{-2^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 1^0}$
$2649 := \frac{2^0 + 6^6 + 4^5 + 9^0}{2^1 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 9^1}$	$2660 := \frac{-2^{12} - 6^0 + 6^6 + 0^0}{2^2 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 0^1}$	$2672 := \frac{-2^0 + 6^4 + 7^4 - 2^{10}}{-2^0 - 6^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$
$2650 := \frac{2^3 + 6^8 + 5^5 + 0^0}{2^2 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 0^1}$	$2661 := \frac{-2^3 + 6^3 + 6^5 - 1^0}{-2^0 - 6^0 + 6^1 - 1^0}$	$2673 := \frac{2^9 + 6^5 + 7^4 + 3^1}{2^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$
$2650 := \frac{2^3 + 6^8 + 5^5 + 0^0}{2^2 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 0^1}$	$2662 := \frac{2^3 + 6^5 + 6^5 + 2^{14}}{2^0 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 2^2}$	$2673 := \frac{2^9 + 6^5 + 7^4 + 3^1}{2^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$
$2651 := \frac{2^6 + 6^3 + 5^6 + 1^0}{-2^0 + 6^0 + 5^1 + 1^0}$	$2662 := \frac{2^3 + 6^5 + 6^5 + 2^{14}}{2^0 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 2^2}$	$2674 := \frac{2^1 + 6^0 + 7^6 + 4^1}{2^5 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 4^1}$
$2652 := \frac{-2^0 - 6^3 + 5^5 - 2^8}{-2^0 - 6^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$	$2663 := \frac{2^{13} + 6^0 + 6^5 + 3^2}{2^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$	$2675 := \frac{2^{17} + 6^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}{2^0 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 5^1}$

$$2675 := \frac{2^{17} + 6^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}{2^0 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2676 := \frac{-2^{11} + 6^0 + 7^5 + 6^4}{-2^0 - 6^0 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2677 := \frac{2^3 + 6^5 + 7^7 + 7^8}{2^3 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 7^4}$$

$$2677 := \frac{2^3 + 6^5 + 7^7 + 7^8}{2^3 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 7^4}$$

$$2678 := \frac{2^8 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 8^0}{2^0 + 6^0 - 7^1 + 8^1}$$

$$2679 := \frac{2^{13} + 6^7 + 7^0 + 9^4}{2^4 + 6^1 + 7^1 + 9^2}$$

$$2679 := \frac{2^{13} + 6^7 + 7^0 + 9^4}{2^4 + 6^1 + 7^1 + 9^2}$$

$$2680 := \frac{2^8 + 6^5 + 8^1 + 0^1}{2^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2680 := \frac{2^8 + 6^5 + 8^1 + 0^1}{2^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2681 := \frac{2^{11} + 6^2 + 8^5 + 1^0}{-2^1 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 1^0}$$

$$2682 := \frac{2^6 + 6^2 + 8^4 + 2^{16}}{2^0 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 2^4}$$

$$2682 := \frac{2^6 + 6^2 + 8^4 + 2^{16}}{2^0 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 2^4}$$

$$2683 := \frac{2^{11} + 6^2 + 8^5 + 3^3}{2^0 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2683 := \frac{2^{11} + 6^2 + 8^5 + 3^3}{2^0 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2684 := \frac{2^{19} + 6^5 + 8^6 + 4^4}{2^3 + 6^3 + 8^1 + 4^3}$$

$$2684 := \frac{2^{19} + 6^5 + 8^6 + 4^4}{2^3 + 6^3 + 8^1 + 4^3}$$

$$2685 := \frac{2^{17} + 6^5 + 8^3 + 5^7}{2^5 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2685 := \frac{2^{17} + 6^5 + 8^3 + 5^7}{2^5 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2686 := \frac{2^{14} + 6^1 + 8^1 + 6^5}{2^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2686 := \frac{2^{14} + 6^1 + 8^1 + 6^5}{2^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2687 := \frac{2^{10} + 6^6 + 8^0 + 7^5}{2^3 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$2687 := \frac{2^{10} + 6^6 + 8^0 + 7^5}{2^3 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$2688 := \frac{2^8 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 8^4}{2^1 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 8^1}$$

$$2688 := \frac{2^8 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 8^4}{2^1 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 8^1}$$

$$2689 := \frac{2^{16} + 6^1 + 8^5 + 9^4}{2^0 + 6^2 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2689 := \frac{2^{16} + 6^1 + 8^5 + 9^4}{2^0 + 6^2 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2690 := \frac{2^{10} + 6^5 - 9^3 - 0^0}{2^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2691 := \frac{2^{12} + 6^4 - 9^1 - 1^0}{-2^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2692 := \frac{2^0 + 6^4 - 9^1 + 2^{12}}{-2^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$2693 := \frac{2^{17} + 6^3 + 9^4 + 3^7}{2^2 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2693 := \frac{2^{17} + 6^3 + 9^4 + 3^7}{2^2 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2694 := \frac{2^1 + 6^3 + 9^5 + 4^0}{2^2 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 4^2}$$

$$2694 := \frac{2^1 + 6^3 + 9^5 + 4^0}{2^2 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 4^2}$$

$$2695 := \frac{2^{15} + 6^2 + 9^2 + 5^6}{2^1 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2695 := \frac{2^{15} + 6^2 + 9^2 + 5^6}{2^1 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2696 := \frac{2^8 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 6^1}{2^0 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 6^1}$$

$$2696 := \frac{2^8 + 6^0 + 9^5 + 6^1}{2^0 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 6^1}$$

$$2697 := \frac{2^{17} + 6^4 + 9^2 + 7^4}{2^2 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2697 := \frac{2^{17} + 6^4 + 9^2 + 7^4}{2^2 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2698 := \frac{2^{17} - 6^2 + 9^4 + 8^0}{2^1 - 6^1 - 9^1 + 8^2}$$

$$2699 := \frac{2^{19} + 6^6 + 9^2 + 9^4}{2^4 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 9^2}$$

$$2699 := \frac{2^{19} + 6^6 + 9^2 + 9^4}{2^4 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 9^2}$$

$$2702 := \frac{2^7 + 7^4 + 0^0 + 2^{14}}{2^0 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 2^2}$$

$$2702 := \frac{2^7 + 7^4 + 0^0 + 2^{14}}{2^0 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 2^2}$$

$$2703 := \frac{2^{13} - 7^0 - 0^0 - 3^4}{2^0 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 3^0}$$

$$2704 := \frac{2^{15} + 7^4 - 0^0 - 4^2}{2^1 + 7^1 + 0^1 + 4^1}$$

$$2705 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^3 + 0^1 - 5^5}{-2^0 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 5^0}$$

$$2706 := \frac{-2^0 + 7^3 + 0^1 + 6^5}{2^0 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2707 := \frac{2^8 + 7^2 + 0^0 + 7^4}{-2^0 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2708 := \frac{2^{20} + 7^4 - 0^0 - 8^5}{2^5 + 7^3 + 0^1 + 8^0}$$

$$2709 := \frac{2^{14} - 7^2 + 0^1 - 9^2}{2^2 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 9^0}$$

$$2712 := \frac{2^7 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 2^{11}}{2^0 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 2^2}$$

$$2712 := \frac{2^7 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 2^{11}}{2^0 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 2^2}$$

$$2713 := \frac{2^{13} - 7^2 - 1^0 - 3^1}{2^1 - 7^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 2714 := \frac{2^{12} - 7^2 - 1^0 + 4^6}{-2^0 - 7^0 + 1^0 + 4^1} & 2727 := \frac{2^1 + 7^0 + 2^3 + 7^7}{2^5 + 7^1 + 2^8 + 7^1} & 2741 := \frac{2^{10} + 7^5 + 4^6 + 1^0}{2^1 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 1^0} \\
 2715 := \frac{2^{15} + 7^4 + 1^0 + 5^3}{2^2 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 5^0} & 2728 := \frac{-2^0 - 7^3 - 2^{10} + 8^4}{-2^0 - 7^0 + 2^1 + 8^0} & 2742 := \frac{2^7 + 7^1 + 4^0 + 2^{15}}{2^1 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 2^3} \\
 2715 := \frac{2^{15} + 7^4 + 1^0 + 5^3}{2^2 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 5^0} & 2729 := \frac{2^7 + 7^8 + 2^{12} + 9^2}{2^3 + 7^2 + 2^{11} + 9^1} & 2742 := \frac{2^7 + 7^1 + 4^0 + 2^{15}}{2^1 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 2^3} \\
 2716 := \frac{2^{13} - 7^1 - 1^0 - 6^2}{-2^0 - 7^0 - 1^0 + 6^1} & 2729 := \frac{2^7 + 7^8 + 2^{12} + 9^2}{2^3 + 7^2 + 2^{11} + 9^1} & 2743 := \frac{2^4 + 7^2 + 4^7 + 3^2}{2^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 3^1} \\
 2717 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^1 + 1^0 - 7^2}{2^1 - 7^0 + 1^0 + 7^0} & 2730 := \frac{2^{13} - 7^0 - 3^0 + 0^1}{2^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 0^1} & 2743 := \frac{2^4 + 7^2 + 4^7 + 3^2}{2^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 3^1} \\
 2718 := \frac{2^{10} - 7^4 - 1^0 + 8^4}{-2^0 - 7^1 + 1^0 + 8^1} & 2731 := \frac{2^{13} - 7^0 + 3^0 + 1^0}{2^1 - 7^0 + 3^0 + 1^0} & 2744 := \frac{2^5 + 7^2 - 4^0 + 4^7}{-2^0 - 7^0 + 4^1 + 4^1} \\
 2719 := \frac{-2^1 + 7^6 - 1^0 - 9^3}{2^5 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 9^1} & 2732 := \frac{2^2 + 7^0 + 3^1 + 2^{14}}{2^0 + 7^0 + 3^1 + 2^0} & 2745 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^1 + 4^8 + 5^5}{2^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 5^2} \\
 2720 := \frac{2^6 + 7^4 + 2^8 - 0^0}{-2^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 0^1} & 2733 := \frac{2^7 + 7^5 + 3^2 + 3^7}{2^1 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 3^1} & 2745 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^1 + 4^8 + 5^5}{2^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 5^2} \\
 2721 := \frac{-2^3 - 7^2 + 2^{14} - 1^0}{2^1 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 1^0} & 2734 := \frac{2^2 + 7^1 + 3^2 + 4^7}{2^0 + 7^0 + 3^1 + 4^0} & 2746 := \frac{2^0 + 7^5 + 4^8 + 6^2}{2^0 + 7^1 + 4^2 + 6^1} \\
 2722 := \frac{2^0 + 7^4 + 2^6 + 2^8}{-2^0 - 7^0 + 2^0 + 2^1} & 2734 := \frac{2^2 + 7^1 + 3^2 + 4^7}{2^0 + 7^0 + 3^1 + 4^0} & 2747 := \frac{2^{10} + 7^2 + 4^6 + 7^5}{2^1 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 7^0} \\
 2723 := \frac{2^9 + 7^0 + 2^{13} + 3^7}{2^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 3^0} & 2735 := \frac{2^6 + 7^5 + 3^6 + 5^7}{2^1 + 7^0 + 3^3 + 5^1} & 2748 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^2 + 4^1 - 8^0}{-2^0 - 7^0 + 4^1 + 8^0} \\
 2723 := \frac{2^9 + 7^0 + 2^{13} + 3^7}{2^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 3^0} & 2736 := \frac{2^{11} + 7^5 + 3^4 + 6^3}{2^1 + 7^0 + 3^1 + 6^0} & 2749 := \frac{2^4 + 7^3 + 4^8 + 9^2}{2^2 + 7^1 + 4^1 + 9^1} \\
 2724 := \frac{2^1 + 7^4 + 2^{17} + 4^0}{2^4 + 7^0 + 2^4 + 4^2} & 2737 := \frac{2^{15} + 7^4 + 3^3 + 7^5}{2^1 + 7^1 + 3^1 + 7^1} & 2749 := \frac{2^4 + 7^3 + 4^8 + 9^2}{2^2 + 7^1 + 4^1 + 9^1} \\
 2724 := \frac{2^1 + 7^4 + 2^{17} + 4^0}{2^4 + 7^0 + 2^4 + 4^2} & 2737 := \frac{2^{15} + 7^4 + 3^3 + 7^5}{2^1 + 7^1 + 3^1 + 7^1} & 2750 := \frac{-2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 0^1}{-2^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 0^1} \\
 2725 := \frac{2^{12} + 7^5 + 2^{17} + 5^4}{2^0 + 7^2 + 2^0 + 5^1} & 2738 := \frac{2^{11} + 7^2 + 3^6 + 8^5}{2^0 + 7^0 + 3^1 + 8^1} & 2751 := \frac{-2^5 - 7^3 + 5^5 + 1^0}{-2^1 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 1^0} \\
 2725 := \frac{2^{12} + 7^5 + 2^{17} + 5^4}{2^0 + 7^2 + 2^0 + 5^1} & 2739 := \frac{2^{17} + 7^4 + 3^2 + 9^3}{2^5 + 7^1 + 3^0 + 9^1} & 2752 := \frac{2^1 + 7^0 + 5^3 + 2^{14}}{2^1 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 2^1} \\
 2726 := \frac{-2^0 - 7^1 + 2^{13} - 6^1}{-2^0 - 7^0 - 2^0 + 6^1} & 2740 := \frac{2^3 + 7^2 + 4^7 - 0^0}{2^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 0^1} & 2752 := \frac{2^1 + 7^0 + 5^3 + 2^{14}}{2^1 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 2^1} \\
 2727 := \frac{2^1 + 7^0 + 2^3 + 7^7}{2^5 + 7^1 + 2^8 + 7^1} & 2741 := \frac{2^{10} + 7^5 + 4^6 + 1^0}{2^1 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 1^0} & 2753 := \frac{2^{12} + 7^2 + 5^3 + 3^{10}}{2^1 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 3^2}
 \end{array}$$

$$2754 := \frac{2^{15} + 7^2 + 5^5 + 4^7}{2^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 4^2}$$

$$2754 := \frac{2^{15} + 7^2 + 5^5 + 4^7}{2^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 4^2}$$

$$2755 := \frac{2^1 + 7^7 + 5^5 + 5^9}{2^4 + 7^3 + 5^2 + 5^4}$$

$$2755 := \frac{2^1 + 7^7 + 5^5 + 5^9}{2^4 + 7^3 + 5^2 + 5^4}$$

$$2756 := \frac{2^6 + 7^1 + 5^3 + 6^6}{2^2 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2756 := \frac{2^6 + 7^1 + 5^3 + 6^6}{2^2 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2757 := \frac{2^9 + 7^5 + 5^3 + 7^6}{2^4 + 7^0 + 5^2 + 7^1}$$

$$2758 := \frac{2^6 + 7^5 + 5^1 + 8^5}{2^1 + 7^1 + 5^0 + 8^1}$$

$$2758 := \frac{2^6 + 7^5 + 5^1 + 8^5}{2^1 + 7^1 + 5^0 + 8^1}$$

$$2759 := \frac{2^{17} + 7^4 + 5^1 + 9^6}{2^7 + 7^1 + 5^2 + 9^2}$$

$$2759 := \frac{2^{17} + 7^4 + 5^1 + 9^6}{2^7 + 7^1 + 5^2 + 9^2}$$

$$2760 := \frac{2^8 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 0^0}{2^0 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 0^0}$$

$$2760 := \frac{2^8 + 7^5 + 6^5 + 0^0}{2^0 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 0^0}$$

$$2761 := \frac{-2^1 + 7^6 + 6^7 + 1^0}{2^4 + 7^3 - 6^3 + 1^0}$$

$$2762 := \frac{2^5 + 7^3 + 6^0 + 2^{15}}{2^0 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 2^2}$$

$$2762 := \frac{2^5 + 7^3 + 6^0 + 2^{15}}{2^0 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 2^2}$$

$$2763 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^4 + 6^3 + 3^5}{2^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2763 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^4 + 6^3 + 3^5}{2^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2764 := \frac{2^6 + 7^7 + 6^0 + 4^3}{2^5 + 7^2 + 6^3 + 4^0}$$

$$2764 := \frac{2^6 + 7^7 + 6^0 + 4^3}{2^5 + 7^2 + 6^3 + 4^0}$$

$$2765 := \frac{2^0 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 5^1}{2^2 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2765 := \frac{2^0 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 5^1}{2^2 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2766 := \frac{-2^0 + 7^5 + 6^1 - 6^3}{-2^0 + 7^1 - 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2767 := \frac{2^{14} + 7^1 + 6^1 + 7^5}{2^2 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2767 := \frac{2^{14} + 7^1 + 6^1 + 7^5}{2^2 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2768 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^2 - 6^0 + 8^2}{-2^0 - 7^0 + 6^1 - 8^0}$$

$$2769 := \frac{2^{14} + 7^5 + 6^2 + 9^0}{2^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2769 := \frac{2^{14} + 7^5 + 6^2 + 9^0}{2^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2770 := \frac{2^{14} + 7^2 + 7^5 + 0^1}{2^2 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 0^1}$$

$$2770 := \frac{2^{14} + 7^2 + 7^5 + 0^1}{2^2 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 0^1}$$

$$2772 := \frac{-2^2 + 7^3 + 7^4 + 2^5}{-2^0 - 7^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2773 := \frac{2^{17} + 7^4 + 7^4 + 3^1}{2^3 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 3^3}$$

$$2774 := \frac{-2^6 - 7^2 - 7^4 + 4^7}{2^1 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2775 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^4 + 7^5 + 5^5}{2^1 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2775 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^4 + 7^5 + 5^5}{2^1 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2776 := \frac{2^3 + 7^4 + 7^5 + 6^3}{2^2 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2776 := \frac{2^3 + 7^4 + 7^5 + 6^3}{2^2 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2777 := \frac{2^5 + 7^0 + 7^3 + 7^4}{-2^1 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2778 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^1 + 7^4 + 8^3}{2^0 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2778 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^1 + 7^4 + 8^3}{2^0 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2779 := \frac{2^{11} + 7^0 + 7^0 + 9^3}{-2^1 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2779 := \frac{2^{11} + 7^0 + 7^0 + 9^3}{-2^1 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2780 := \frac{-2^6 + 7^5 - 8^2 + 0^0}{2^2 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2781 := \frac{-2^7 + 7^5 + 8^1 - 1^0}{-2^0 + 7^1 - 8^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2782 := \frac{-2^0 + 7^4 + 8^2 + 2^{17}}{2^0 + 7^1 + 8^1 + 2^5}$$

$$2783 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^4 + 8^3 + 3^3}{2^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2783 := \frac{2^{13} + 7^4 + 8^3 + 3^3}{2^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$2784 := \frac{2^3 + 7^7 + 8^3 + 4^0}{2^5 + 7^1 + 8^0 + 4^4}$$

$$2784 := \frac{2^3 + 7^7 + 8^3 + 4^0}{2^5 + 7^1 + 8^0 + 4^4}$$

$$2785 := \frac{2^{15} + 7^6 + 8^5 + 5^4}{2^2 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2785 := \frac{2^{15} + 7^6 + 8^5 + 5^4}{2^2 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2786 := \frac{-2^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 6^0}{2^0 - 7^1 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2787 := \frac{2^5 + 7^2 + 8^5 + 7^6}{2^5 + 7^1 + 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$2787 := \frac{2^5 + 7^2 + 8^5 + 7^6}{2^5 + 7^1 + 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$2788 := \frac{-2^4 + 7^5 + 8^0 - 8^2}{-2^0 + 7^1 - 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2789 := \frac{2^{17} + 7^8 + 8^2 + 9^1}{2^{11} + 7^0 + 8^2 + 9^0}$$

$$2789 := \frac{2^{17} + 7^8 + 8^2 + 9^1}{2^{11} + 7^0 + 8^2 + 9^0}$$

$$2790 := \frac{2^9 + 7^6 - 9^4 + 0^1}{2^5 + 7^1 + 9^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2792 := \frac{2^4 + 7^3 + 9^1 + 2^{14}}{2^1 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2792 := \frac{2^4 + 7^3 + 9^1 + 2^{14}}{2^1 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2793 := \frac{2^{15} + 7^3 + 9^1 + 3^{10}}{2^2 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 3^3}$$

$$2793 := \frac{2^{15} + 7^3 + 9^1 + 3^{10}}{2^2 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 3^3}$$

$$2794 := \frac{2^9 + 7^1 + 9^4 + 4^6}{2^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2795 := \frac{2^{14} + 7^1 + 9^5 + 5^2}{2^4 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2795 := \frac{2^{14} + 7^1 + 9^5 + 5^2}{2^4 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2796 := \frac{2^{15} + 7^2 + 9^3 + 6^1}{2^0 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2796 := \frac{2^{15} + 7^2 + 9^3 + 6^1}{2^0 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2797 := \frac{2^{14} + 7^0 + 9^0 - 7^4}{2^1 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2798 := \frac{2^{14} + 7^2 + 9^5 + 8^2}{2^4 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 8^0}$$

$$2798 := \frac{2^{14} + 7^2 + 9^5 + 8^2}{2^4 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 8^0}$$

$$2799 := \frac{2^{11} + 7^5 + 9^1 + 9^3}{2^2 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2799 := \frac{2^{11} + 7^5 + 9^1 + 9^3}{2^2 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2803 := \frac{2^{11} + 8^3 + 0^1 + 3^5}{-2^0 + 8^0 + 0^1 + 3^0}$$

$$2804 := \frac{2^{19} + 8^2 + 0^1 - 4^1}{-2^2 - 8^2 - 0^0 + 4^4}$$

$$2805 := \frac{-2^8 - 8^2 + 0^1 + 5^5}{-2^0 + 8^0 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2806 := \frac{2^{16} + 8^3 + 0^1 + 6^4}{2^4 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2806 := \frac{2^{16} + 8^3 + 0^1 + 6^4}{2^4 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2807 := \frac{2^0 - 8^6 + 0^1 + 7^7}{2^7 + 8^2 + 0^0 + 7^1}$$

$$2809 := \frac{2^{17} + 8^1 + 0^1 + 9^4}{2^5 + 8^1 + 0^1 + 9^1}$$

$$2809 := \frac{2^{17} + 8^1 + 0^1 + 9^4}{2^5 + 8^1 + 0^1 + 9^1}$$

$$2813 := \frac{-2^0 + 8^1 + 1^0 + 3^9}{2^1 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 3^1}$$

$$2815 := \frac{2^{14} + 8^3 - 1^0 - 5^1}{-2^0 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 5^1}$$

$$2816 := \frac{2^{14} + 8^3 - 1^0 + 6^0}{-2^1 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2817 := \frac{2^5 + 8^2 - 1^0 + 7^5}{-2^0 - 8^0 + 1^0 + 7^1}$$

$$2819 := \frac{-2^7 + 8^6 + 1^0 - 9^5}{-2^1 - 8^1 + 1^0 + 9^2}$$

$$2821 := \frac{-2^5 - 8^4 + 2^{17} + 1^0}{2^2 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 1^0}$$

$$2822 := \frac{2^2 + 8^3 + 2^5 + 2^{14}}{2^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 2^1}$$

$$2822 := \frac{2^2 + 8^3 + 2^5 + 2^{14}}{2^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 2^1}$$

$$2823 := \frac{2^7 + 8^5 + 2^{17} + 3^{10}}{2^1 + 8^2 + 2^2 + 3^2}$$

$$2823 := \frac{2^7 + 8^5 + 2^{17} + 3^{10}}{2^1 + 8^2 + 2^2 + 3^2}$$

$$2824 := \frac{2^4 + 8^3 + 2^5 + 4^7}{2^1 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 4^0}$$

$$2824 := \frac{2^4 + 8^3 + 2^5 + 4^7}{2^1 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 4^0}$$

$$2825 := \frac{2^{14} + 8^5 + 2^{15} + 5^1}{2^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 5^2}$$

$$2825 := \frac{2^{14} + 8^5 + 2^{15} + 5^1}{2^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 5^2}$$

$$2826 := \frac{2^2 + 8^4 + 2^{14} + 6^5}{2^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 6^1}$$

$$2826 := \frac{2^2 + 8^4 + 2^{14} + 6^5}{2^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 6^1}$$

$$2827 := \frac{2^7 + 8^2 + 2^{20} + 7^2}{2^1 + 8^2 + 2^8 + 7^2}$$

$$2827 := \frac{2^7 + 8^2 + 2^{20} + 7^2}{2^1 + 8^2 + 2^8 + 7^2}$$

$$2828 := \frac{2^3 + 8^2 + 2^{14} + 8^3}{2^1 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$2828 := \frac{2^3 + 8^2 + 2^{14} + 8^3}{2^1 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$2829 := \frac{2^8 + 8^5 + 2^{19} + 9^0}{2^2 + 8^2 + 2^7 + 9^0}$$

$$2829 := \frac{2^8 + 8^5 + 2^{19} + 9^0}{2^2 + 8^2 + 2^7 + 9^0}$$

$$2830 := \frac{-2^{10} + 8^4 - 3^5 + 0^0}{-2^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2831 := \frac{2^0 - 8^5 + 3^{11} + 1^0}{-2^5 + 8^0 + 3^4 + 1^0}$$

$$2832 := \frac{2^0 + 8^4 + 3^{11} + 2^2}{2^2 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 2^5}$$

$$2832 := \frac{2^0 + 8^4 + 3^{11} + 2^2}{2^2 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 2^5}$$

$$2833 := \frac{2^8 + 8^5 + 3^5 + 3^6}{2^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 3^2}$$

$$2833 := \frac{2^8 + 8^5 + 3^5 + 3^6}{2^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 3^2}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 2834 := \frac{2^0 + 8^6 + 3^0 + 4^9}{2^5 + 8^1 + 3^4 + 4^3} & 2846 := \frac{2^7 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 6^1}{2^1 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 6^1} & 2856 := \frac{-2^0 + 8^5 - 5^6 - 6^1}{-2^0 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 6^0} \\
 2834 := \frac{2^0 + 8^6 + 3^0 + 4^9}{2^5 + 8^1 + 3^4 + 4^3} & 2846 := \frac{2^7 + 8^5 + 4^6 + 6^1}{2^1 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 6^1} & 2857 := \frac{2^{16} + 8^0 + 5^3 + 7^2}{2^4 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 7^0} \\
 2835 := \frac{2^{17} + 8^3 + 3^4 + 5^7}{2^1 + 8^2 + 3^1 + 5^1} & 2847 := \frac{2^{15} + 8^5 + 4^9 + 7^5}{2^2 + 8^2 + 4^1 + 7^2} & 2857 := \frac{2^{16} + 8^0 + 5^3 + 7^2}{2^4 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 7^0} \\
 2835 := \frac{2^{17} + 8^3 + 3^4 + 5^7}{2^1 + 8^2 + 3^1 + 5^1} & 2847 := \frac{2^{15} + 8^5 + 4^9 + 7^5}{2^2 + 8^2 + 4^1 + 7^2} & 2858 := \frac{2^2 + 8^0 - 5^6 + 8^5}{-2^0 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 8^0} \\
 2836 := \frac{2^{12} + 8^5 + 3^1 + 6^0}{2^0 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 6^0} & 2848 := \frac{2^{11} + 8^2 + 4^7 + 8^5}{2^0 + 8^1 + 4^0 + 8^1} & 2859 := \frac{2^4 + 8^6 + 5^2 + 9^4}{2^2 + 8^1 + 5^0 + 9^2} \\
 2836 := \frac{2^{12} + 8^5 + 3^1 + 6^0}{2^0 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 6^0} & 2848 := \frac{2^{11} + 8^2 + 4^7 + 8^5}{2^0 + 8^1 + 4^0 + 8^1} & 2859 := \frac{2^4 + 8^6 + 5^2 + 9^4}{2^2 + 8^1 + 5^0 + 9^2} \\
 2837 := \frac{2^{13} + 8^3 + 3^5 + 7^4}{2^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 7^0} & 2849 := \frac{2^{11} + 8^6 + 4^9 + 9^3}{2^5 + 8^1 + 4^3 + 9^2} & 2860 := \frac{2^8 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 0^1}{2^1 + 8^1 + 6^0 + 0^0} \\
 2837 := \frac{2^{13} + 8^3 + 3^5 + 7^4}{2^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 7^0} & 2849 := \frac{2^{11} + 8^6 + 4^9 + 9^3}{2^5 + 8^1 + 4^3 + 9^2} & 2860 := \frac{2^8 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 0^1}{2^1 + 8^1 + 6^0 + 0^0} \\
 2838 := \frac{2^7 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 8^7}{2^0 + 8^0 + 3^6 + 8^1} & 2850 := \frac{2^{16} + 8^1 + 5^1 + 0^0}{2^4 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 0^0} & 2861 := \frac{-2^1 + 8^5 - 6^4 + 1^0}{2^0 + 8^1 + 6^0 + 1^0} \\
 2838 := \frac{2^7 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 8^7}{2^0 + 8^0 + 3^6 + 8^1} & 2850 := \frac{2^{16} + 8^1 + 5^1 + 0^0}{2^4 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 0^0} & 2862 := \frac{2^5 + 8^3 + 6^2 + 2^{17}}{2^0 + 8^0 + 6^2 + 2^3} \\
 2839 := \frac{2^{11} + 8^4 + 3^{13} + 9^3}{2^4 + 8^3 + 3^3 + 9^1} & 2851 := \frac{2^{15} + 8^5 + 5^8 - 1^0}{2^7 + 8^1 + 5^2 - 1^0} & 2862 := \frac{2^5 + 8^3 + 6^2 + 2^{17}}{2^0 + 8^0 + 6^2 + 2^3} \\
 2839 := \frac{2^{11} + 8^4 + 3^{13} + 9^3}{2^4 + 8^3 + 3^3 + 9^1} & 2852 := \frac{-2^4 - 8^0 + 5^5 - 2^8}{-2^0 - 8^0 + 5^0 + 2^1} & 2863 := \frac{2^8 + 8^4 + 6^5 + 3^7}{2^1 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 3^0} \\
 2841 := \frac{-2^7 - 8^2 + 4^8 - 1^0}{-2^1 + 8^1 + 4^2 + 1^0} & 2853 := \frac{2^3 + 8^1 + 5^5 + 3^9}{2^0 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 3^0} & 2864 := \frac{2^{17} + 8^4 + 6^5 + 4^4}{2^1 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 4^1} \\
 2842 := \frac{2^2 - 8^4 - 4^4 + 2^{15}}{2^0 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 2^2} & 2853 := \frac{2^3 + 8^1 + 5^5 + 3^9}{2^0 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 3^0} & 2865 := \frac{2^6 + 8^4 - 6^4 + 5^0}{2^0 + 8^0 - 6^1 + 5^1} \\
 2843 := \frac{2^2 + 8^2 + 4^9 + 3^7}{2^2 + 8^2 + 4^2 + 3^2} & 2854 := \frac{2^0 + 8^4 + 5^6 + 4^4}{2^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 4^1} & 2866 := \frac{2^{17} + 8^3 + 6^2 + 6^3}{2^0 + 8^1 + 6^0 + 6^2} \\
 2844 := \frac{-2^{13} + 8^5 - 4^1 + 4^5}{-2^0 + 8^1 + 4^0 + 4^0} & 2854 := \frac{2^0 + 8^4 + 5^6 + 4^4}{2^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 4^1} & 2866 := \frac{2^{17} + 8^3 + 6^2 + 6^3}{2^0 + 8^1 + 6^0 + 6^2} \\
 2845 := \frac{2^1 + 8^6 + 4^7 + 5^5}{2^1 + 8^1 + 4^3 + 5^2} & 2855 := \frac{2^{17} + 8^1 + 5^3 + 5^3}{2^3 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 5^2} & 2867 := \frac{2^{15} + 8^6 + 6^6 + 7^5}{2^5 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 7^2} \\
 2845 := \frac{2^1 + 8^6 + 4^7 + 5^5}{2^1 + 8^1 + 4^3 + 5^2} & 2855 := \frac{2^{17} + 8^1 + 5^3 + 5^3}{2^3 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 5^2} & 2867 := \frac{2^{15} + 8^6 + 6^6 + 7^5}{2^5 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 7^2}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 2868 := \frac{2^3 + 8^3 + 6^8 + 8^3}{2^2 + 8^2 + 6^1 + 8^3} & 2881 := \frac{-2^{16} - 8^3 + 8^7 + 1^0}{2^7 + 8^2 + 8^3 + 1^0} & 2892 := \frac{-2^0 - 8^4 + 9^5 - 2^2}{2^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 2^4} \\
 2868 := \frac{2^3 + 8^3 + 6^8 + 8^3}{2^2 + 8^2 + 6^1 + 8^3} & 2882 := \frac{2^{16} + 8^1 + 8^4 + 2^{20}}{2^2 + 8^2 + 8^2 + 2^8} & 2893 := \frac{2^{11} + 8^6 + 9^4 + 3^{10}}{2^4 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 3^4} \\
 2869 := \frac{2^{17} + 8^2 + 6^5 + 9^5}{2^4 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 9^1} & 2882 := \frac{2^{16} + 8^1 + 8^4 + 2^{20}}{2^2 + 8^2 + 8^2 + 2^8} & 2893 := \frac{2^{11} + 8^6 + 9^4 + 3^{10}}{2^4 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 3^4} \\
 2869 := \frac{2^{17} + 8^2 + 6^5 + 9^5}{2^4 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 9^1} & 2883 := \frac{2^6 + 8^2 + 8^6 + 3^4}{2^0 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 3^4} & 2894 := \frac{2^{10} + 8^0 + 9^0 + 4^8}{2^1 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 4^1} \\
 2871 := \frac{-2^{13} - 8^0 + 7^5 - 1^0}{2^0 + 8^1 - 7^1 + 1^0} & 2883 := \frac{2^6 + 8^2 + 8^6 + 3^4}{2^0 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 3^4} & 2894 := \frac{2^{10} + 8^0 + 9^0 + 4^8}{2^1 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 4^1} \\
 2872 := \frac{2^0 + 8^3 + 7^1 + 2^{16}}{2^2 + 8^1 + 7^1 + 2^2} & 2884 := \frac{2^3 + 8^4 + 8^6 + 4^7}{2^5 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 4^3} & 2895 := \frac{2^{16} + 8^5 + 9^0 + 5^3}{2^4 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 5^0} \\
 2872 := \frac{2^0 + 8^3 + 7^1 + 2^{16}}{2^2 + 8^1 + 7^1 + 2^2} & 2884 := \frac{2^3 + 8^4 + 8^6 + 4^7}{2^5 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 4^3} & 2895 := \frac{2^{16} + 8^5 + 9^0 + 5^3}{2^4 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 5^0} \\
 2873 := \frac{2^{13} + 8^3 + 7^3 + 3^9}{2^0 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 3^0} & 2885 := \frac{2^2 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 5^9}{2^5 + 8^1 + 8^3 + 5^3} & 2896 := \frac{-2^8 - 8^3 + 9^4 - 6^0}{-2^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 6^0} \\
 2873 := \frac{2^{13} + 8^3 + 7^3 + 3^9}{2^0 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 3^0} & 2885 := \frac{2^2 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 5^9}{2^5 + 8^1 + 8^3 + 5^3} & 2897 := \frac{2^{20} + 8^1 + 9^2 + 7^2}{2^1 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 7^3} \\
 2874 := \frac{-2^{13} + 8^1 + 7^5 - 4^0}{-2^0 - 8^0 + 7^0 + 4^1} & 2886 := \frac{-2^{10} + 8^0 + 8^5 + 6^0}{2^0 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 6^0} & 2897 := \frac{2^{20} + 8^1 + 9^2 + 7^2}{2^1 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 7^3} \\
 2875 := \frac{2^{19} + 8^6 + 7^7 + 5^2}{2^4 + 8^3 + 7^1 + 5^2} & 2887 := \frac{2^{10} + 8^2 + 8^6 + 7^5}{2^5 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 7^2} & 2898 := \frac{2^{13} - 8^0 - 9^1 + 8^3}{2^0 + 8^0 + 9^1 - 8^1} \\
 2875 := \frac{2^{19} + 8^6 + 7^7 + 5^2}{2^4 + 8^3 + 7^1 + 5^2} & 2887 := \frac{2^{10} + 8^2 + 8^6 + 7^5}{2^5 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 7^2} & 2899 := \frac{2^{10} - 8^5 - 9^5 + 9^6}{-2^1 - 8^1 + 9^2 + 9^2} \\
 2876 := \frac{2^{13} + 8^6 + 7^1 + 6^0}{2^0 + 8^1 + 7^2 + 6^2} & 2888 := \frac{2^{14} + 8^1 - 8^2 + 8^5}{2^1 - 8^0 + 8^1 + 8^1} & 2902 := \frac{2^9 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 2^{13}}{2^0 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 2^0} \\
 2876 := \frac{2^{13} + 8^6 + 7^1 + 6^0}{2^0 + 8^1 + 7^2 + 6^2} & 2889 := \frac{2^7 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 9^4}{2^3 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 9^0} & 2902 := \frac{2^9 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 2^{13}}{2^0 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 2^0} \\
 2877 := \frac{-2^3 + 8^3 - 7^2 + 7^5}{-2^0 - 8^0 + 7^0 + 7^1} & 2889 := \frac{2^7 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 9^4}{2^3 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 9^0} & 2903 := \frac{2^{16} + 9^5 + 0^0 + 3^5}{2^5 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 3^2} \\
 2878 := \frac{2^{17} - 8^0 - 7^3 - 8^4}{2^1 + 8^0 + 7^2 - 8^1} & 2890 := \frac{2^6 + 8^6 + 9^4 + 0^0}{2^2 + 8^1 + 9^2 + 0^1} & 2903 := \frac{2^{16} + 9^5 + 0^0 + 3^5}{2^5 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 3^2} \\
 2879 := \frac{2^{11} + 8^4 + 7^3 - 9^3}{-2^0 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 9^0} & 2890 := \frac{2^6 + 8^6 + 9^4 + 0^0}{2^2 + 8^1 + 9^2 + 0^1} & 2904 := \frac{-2^5 - 9^4 + 0^0 + 4^9}{2^1 + 9^2 + 0^0 + 4^1} \\
 2880 := \frac{2^{13} - 8^2 + 8^3 + 0^1}{2^0 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 0^1} & 2891 := \frac{2^{16} + 8^5 - 9^1 - 1^0}{2^4 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 1^0} & 2905 := \frac{-2^{11} + 9^5 - 0^0 + 5^6}{-2^0 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 5^2}
 \end{array}$$

$$2906 := \frac{2^{10} - 9^2 - 0^0 + 6^5}{2^0 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2907 := \frac{2^{15} + 9^4 + 0^1 + 7^6}{2^2 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 7^2}$$

$$2907 := \frac{2^{15} + 9^4 + 0^1 + 7^6}{2^2 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 7^2}$$

$$2908 := \frac{2^{11} + 9^2 - 0^0 + 8^5}{2^0 + 9^1 + 0^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2909 := \frac{2^{11} - 9^1 + 0^0 + 9^5}{2^1 + 9^1 + 0^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2912 := \frac{2^7 + 9^4 - 1^0 + 2^{11}}{-2^0 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2913 := \frac{2^{17} + 9^1 + 1^0 + 3^1}{2^3 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 3^3}$$

$$2913 := \frac{2^{17} + 9^1 + 1^0 + 3^1}{2^3 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 3^3}$$

$$2914 := \frac{2^{12} - 9^2 - 1^0 + 4^7}{2^0 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$2915 := \frac{-2^7 - 9^2 - 1^0 + 5^5}{-2^1 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$2916 := \frac{-2^9 + 9^4 - 1^0 - 6^3}{-2^0 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2917 := \frac{2^{15} - 9^3 - 1^0 + 7^2}{2^1 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 7^1}$$

$$2918 := \frac{2^7 + 9^8 - 1^0 - 8^3}{2^{12} + 9^4 - 1^0 + 8^4}$$

$$2919 := \frac{-2^{15} - 9^1 - 1^0 + 9^5}{-2^1 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2920 := \frac{2^{10} + 9^4 + 2^{12} - 0^0}{2^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 0^0}$$

$$2921 := \frac{2^9 + 9^5 + 2^{14} + 1^0}{2^3 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 1^0}$$

$$2921 := \frac{2^9 + 9^5 + 2^{14} + 1^0}{2^3 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 1^0}$$

$$2922 := \frac{2^0 + 9^5 + 2^4 - 2^{15}}{2^1 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 2^2}$$

$$2923 := \frac{2^9 + 9^3 + 2^{17} + 3^9}{2^1 + 9^1 + 2^5 + 3^2}$$

$$2923 := \frac{2^9 + 9^3 + 2^{17} + 3^9}{2^1 + 9^1 + 2^5 + 3^2}$$

$$2924 := \frac{-2^0 + 9^3 + 2^{10} + 4^6}{-2^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2925 := \frac{2^7 + 9^5 + 2^{11} + 5^5}{2^2 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$2925 := \frac{2^7 + 9^5 + 2^{11} + 5^5}{2^2 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$2926 := \frac{2^{12} + 9^0 + 2^{14} + 6^0}{2^0 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 6^0}$$

$$2926 := \frac{2^{12} + 9^0 + 2^{14} + 6^0}{2^0 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 6^0}$$

$$2927 := \frac{2^4 + 9^4 + 2^5 + 7^5}{2^1 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$2927 := \frac{2^4 + 9^4 + 2^5 + 7^5}{2^1 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$2928 := \frac{-2^0 + 9^2 + 2^{13} + 8^3}{-2^0 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$2929 := \frac{2^3 + 9^3 + 2^{18} + 9^3}{2^2 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 9^2}$$

$$2929 := \frac{2^3 + 9^3 + 2^{18} + 9^3}{2^2 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 9^2}$$

$$2930 := \frac{-2^{11} + 9^4 + 3^{11} + 0^1}{2^3 + 9^2 - 3^3 + 0^1}$$

$$2931 := \frac{2^4 + 9^3 + 3^7 - 1^0}{-2^1 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2932 := \frac{2^4 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 2^7}{2^0 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 2^2}$$

$$2933 := \frac{2^{16} + 9^3 + 3^3 + 3^{11}}{2^6 + 9^0 + 3^2 + 3^2}$$

$$2934 := \frac{2^{13} + 9^5 + 3^7 + 4^8}{2^1 + 9^0 + 3^3 + 4^2}$$

$$2935 := \frac{2^3 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 5^3}{2^1 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2935 := \frac{2^3 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 5^3}{2^1 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2936 := \frac{2^{11} + 9^9 + 3^5 + 6^2}{2^{16} + 9^2 + 3^9 + 6^6}$$

$$2936 := \frac{2^{11} + 9^9 + 3^5 + 6^2}{2^{16} + 9^2 + 3^9 + 6^6}$$

$$2937 := \frac{2^{13} + 9^5 + 3^{10} + 7^0}{2^3 + 9^0 + 3^3 + 7^1}$$

$$2937 := \frac{2^{13} + 9^5 + 3^{10} + 7^0}{2^3 + 9^0 + 3^3 + 7^1}$$

$$2938 := \frac{2^{14} + 9^3 + 3^1 + 8^3}{2^0 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 8^0}$$

$$2938 := \frac{2^{14} + 9^3 + 3^1 + 8^3}{2^0 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 8^0}$$

$$2939 := \frac{2^{11} + 9^2 + 3^4 + 9^3}{-2^1 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2940 := \frac{2^{15} + 9^3 - 4^6 - 0^0}{2^2 + 9^0 + 4^1 + 0^0}$$

$$2941 := \frac{-2^{13} + 9^3 + 4^{10} + 1^0}{2^4 + 9^2 + 4^4 + 1^0}$$

$$2942 := \frac{2^0 + 9^2 + 4^8 + 2^{11}}{2^1 + 9^0 + 4^1 + 2^4}$$

$$2942 := \frac{2^0 + 9^2 + 4^8 + 2^{11}}{2^1 + 9^0 + 4^1 + 2^4}$$

$$2943 := \frac{2^5 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 3^{11}}{2^1 + 9^0 + 4^3 + 3^0}$$

$$2943 := \frac{2^5 + 9^4 + 4^7 + 3^{11}}{2^1 + 9^0 + 4^3 + 3^0}$$

$$2944 := \frac{-2^7 - 9^0 + 4^0 + 4^9}{2^3 + 9^0 + 4^2 + 4^3}$$

$$2945 := \frac{2^9 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 5^4}{2^2 + 9^0 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$2945 := \frac{2^9 + 9^5 + 4^7 + 5^4}{2^2 + 9^0 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$2946 := \frac{2^{19} + 9^6 + 4^0 + 6^5}{2^7 + 9^0 + 4^2 + 6^3}$$

$$2946 := \frac{2^{19} + 9^6 + 4^0 + 6^5}{2^7 + 9^0 + 4^2 + 6^3}$$

$$2947 := \frac{2^6 + 9^5 + 4^8 + 7^5}{2^4 + 9^1 + 4^2 + 7^1}$$

$$2947 := \frac{2^6 + 9^5 + 4^8 + 7^5}{2^4 + 9^1 + 4^2 + 7^1}$$

$$2948 := \frac{-2^4 - 9^4 + 4^8 + 8^0}{2^1 + 9^0 + 4^2 + 8^0}$$

$$2949 := \frac{2^9 + 9^3 + 4^7 + 9^5}{2^2 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 9^1}$$

$$2949 := \frac{2^9 + 9^3 + 4^7 + 9^5}{2^2 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 9^1}$$

$$2950 := \frac{2^{14} + 9^6 + 5^6 + 0^1}{2^6 + 9^0 + 5^3 + 0^0}$$

$$2950 := \frac{2^{14} + 9^6 + 5^6 + 0^1}{2^6 + 9^0 + 5^3 + 0^0}$$

$$2951 := \frac{2^{13} + 9^4 + 5^0 + 1^0}{2^1 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2951 := \frac{2^{13} + 9^4 + 5^0 + 1^0}{2^1 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2952 := \frac{2^1 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 2^{13}}{2^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2952 := \frac{2^1 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 2^{13}}{2^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2952 := \frac{-2^4 + 9^4 - 5^4 - 2^4}{2^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 - 2^0}$$

$$2953 := \frac{2^0 + 9^1 + 5^0 + 3^{10}}{2^0 + 9^1 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$2954 := \frac{2^{13} + 9^4 + 5^0 + 4^2}{2^1 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2954 := \frac{2^{13} + 9^4 + 5^0 + 4^2}{2^1 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2955 := \frac{2^0 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 5^2}{2^0 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2955 := \frac{2^0 + 9^5 + 5^2 + 5^2}{2^0 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 5^1}$$

$$2956 := \frac{2^6 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 6^1}{2^2 + 9^1 + 5^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2956 := \frac{2^6 + 9^5 + 5^0 + 6^1}{2^2 + 9^1 + 5^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2957 := \frac{2^{13} + 9^4 + 5^2 + 7^1}{2^1 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2957 := \frac{2^{13} + 9^4 + 5^2 + 7^1}{2^1 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2958 := \frac{2^8 + 9^3 + 5^6 + 8^4}{2^2 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2958 := \frac{2^8 + 9^3 + 5^6 + 8^4}{2^2 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2959 := \frac{2^{17} + 9^3 + 5^4 + 9^3}{2^1 + 9^1 + 5^2 + 9^1}$$

$$2959 := \frac{2^{17} + 9^3 + 5^4 + 9^3}{2^1 + 9^1 + 5^2 + 9^1}$$

$$2960 := \frac{2^{10} + 9^2 + 6^5 - 0^0}{2^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$2961 := \frac{-2^3 + 9^3 + 6^6 - 1^0}{2^3 + 9^0 + 6^1 + 1^0}$$

$$2962 := \frac{2^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 2^{15}}{2^3 + 9^0 + 6^1 + 2^4}$$

$$2962 := \frac{2^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 2^{15}}{2^3 + 9^0 + 6^1 + 2^4}$$

$$2963 := \frac{2^8 + 9^6 + 6^7 + 3^{13}}{2^0 + 9^2 + 6^0 + 3^6}$$

$$2963 := \frac{2^8 + 9^6 + 6^7 + 3^{13}}{2^0 + 9^2 + 6^0 + 3^6}$$

$$2964 := \frac{2^0 - 9^1 + 6^7 - 4^9}{-2^0 + 9^1 - 6^0 - 4^0}$$

$$2965 := \frac{2^7 + 9^4 + 6^6 + 5^2}{2^1 + 9^1 + 6^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2965 := \frac{2^7 + 9^4 + 6^6 + 5^2}{2^1 + 9^1 + 6^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2966 := \frac{2^{12} - 9^1 + 6^0 + 6^5}{2^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2967 := \frac{2^{10} + 9^0 + 6^1 + 7^6}{2^1 + 9^0 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$2967 := \frac{2^{10} + 9^0 + 6^1 + 7^6}{2^1 + 9^0 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$2968 := \frac{-2^0 + 9^0 + 6^5 + 8^4}{2^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2969 := \frac{2^3 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 9^6}{2^4 + 9^2 + 6^0 + 9^2}$$

$$2969 := \frac{2^3 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 9^6}{2^4 + 9^2 + 6^0 + 9^2}$$

$$2970 := \frac{2^3 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 0^1}{2^2 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 0^1}$$

$$2970 := \frac{2^3 + 9^5 + 7^3 + 0^1}{2^2 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 0^1}$$

$$2971 := \frac{2^{13} + 9^3 - 7^1 - 1^0}{2^1 - 9^0 + 7^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2972 := \frac{2^9 + 9^0 + 7^5 + 2^9}{2^1 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2972 := \frac{2^9 + 9^0 + 7^5 + 2^9}{2^1 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2973 := \frac{2^9 + 9^4 + 7^0 + 3^9}{2^2 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 3^1}$$

$$2974 := \frac{2^{12} + 9^2 + 7^6 + 4^8}{2^0 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 4^1}$$

$$2974 := \frac{2^{12} + 9^2 + 7^6 + 4^8}{2^0 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 4^1}$$

$$2975 := \frac{2^{10} + 9^5 + 7^4 + 5^0}{2^2 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2975 := \frac{2^{10} + 9^5 + 7^4 + 5^0}{2^2 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2976 := \frac{2^3 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 6^6}{2^0 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2976 := \frac{2^3 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 6^6}{2^0 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$2977 := \frac{-2^5 + 9^4 + 7^0 + 7^4}{2^1 - 9^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$2978 := \frac{2^{10} + 9^5 + 7^4 + 8^2}{2^2 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 8^0}$$

$$2979 := \frac{2^{13} + 9^1 + 7^1 + 9^3}{2^1 - 9^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$2980 := \frac{2^1 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 0^0}{2^0 + 9^0 + 8^1 + 0^0}$$

$$2980 := \frac{2^1 + 9^1 + 8^5 + 0^0}{2^0 + 9^0 + 8^1 + 0^0}$$

$$2981 := \frac{-2^{13} - 9^3 + 8^5 + 1^0}{-2^0 + 9^1 - 8^0 + 1^0}$$

$$2982 := \frac{2^0 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 2^5}{2^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 2^3}$$

$$2982 := \frac{2^0 + 9^0 + 8^5 + 2^5}{2^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 2^3}$$

$$2983 := \frac{2^3 + 9^4 + 8^1 + 3^{10}}{2^1 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2983 := \frac{2^3 + 9^4 + 8^1 + 3^{10}}{2^1 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 3^1}$$

$$2984 := \frac{2^0 - 9^1 + 8^5 + 4^3}{2^0 + 9^0 + 8^1 + 4^0}$$

$$2985 := \frac{2^{15} + 9^1 + 8^5 + 5^3}{2^2 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2985 := \frac{2^{15} + 9^1 + 8^5 + 5^3}{2^2 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 5^0}$$

$$2986 := \frac{2^0 + 9^1 + 8^4 + 6^6}{2^0 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2986 := \frac{2^0 + 9^1 + 8^4 + 6^6}{2^0 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$2987 := \frac{2^0 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 7^1}{2^0 + 9^0 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2987 := \frac{2^0 + 9^2 + 8^5 + 7^1}{2^0 + 9^0 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$2988 := \frac{2^{16} - 9^5 + 8^0 - 8^3}{-2^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$2989 := \frac{2^0 + 9^3 + 8^0 + 9^5}{2^0 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2989 := \frac{2^0 + 9^3 + 8^0 + 9^5}{2^0 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 9^1}$$

$$2990 := \frac{-2^{13} + 9^0 + 9^6 + 0^1}{2^8 - 9^0 - 9^2 + 0^0}$$

$$2991 := \frac{-2^{13} - 9^1 + 9^5 - 1^0}{-2^1 + 9^1 + 9^1 + 1^0}$$

$$2992 := \frac{2^{10} + 9^0 - 9^2 + 2^{11}}{-2^0 - 9^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$2993 := \frac{2^0 + 9^2 + 9^3 + 3^{10}}{2^0 + 9^0 + 9^1 + 3^2}$$

$$2993 := \frac{2^0 + 9^2 + 9^3 + 3^{10}}{2^0 + 9^0 + 9^1 + 3^2}$$

$$2994 := \frac{2^{15} + 9^2 + 9^2 + 4^1}{2^3 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$2995 := \frac{2^5 - 9^2 - 9^2 + 5^5}{-2^1 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$2996 := \frac{-2^1 + 9^3 + 9^4 - 6^4}{-2^0 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$2997 := \frac{2^{10} - 9^3 + 9^5 - 7^4}{2^1 + 9^0 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$2998 := \frac{2^7 + 9^0 + 9^2 + 8^5}{2^0 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 8^1}$$

$$2998 := \frac{2^7 + 9^0 + 9^2 + 8^5}{2^0 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 8^1}$$

$$2999 := \frac{2^{12} - 9^3 + 9^4 + 9^5}{2^2 + 9^0 + 9^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3002 := \frac{-3^7 - 0^0 + 0^1 + 2^{13}}{3^0 + 0^1 + 0^1 + 2^0}$$

$$3004 := \frac{3^8 - 0^0 + 0^1 + 4^8}{3^2 - 0^0 + 0^1 + 4^2}$$

$$3005 := \frac{3^1 + 0^0 + 0^0 + 5^7}{3^0 + 0^1 + 0^1 + 5^2}$$

$$3005 := \frac{3^1 + 0^0 + 0^0 + 5^7}{3^0 + 0^1 + 0^1 + 5^2}$$

$$3012 := \frac{3^6 + 0^1 - 1^0 + 2^{16}}{-3^2 + 0^1 - 1^0 + 2^5}$$

$$3016 := \frac{3^{10} + 0^1 - 1^0 - 6^5}{3^2 + 0^0 + 1^0 + 6^1}$$

$$3021 := \frac{3^{12} + 0^1 + 2^8 - 1^0}{-3^4 + 0^1 + 2^8 + 1^0}$$

$$3022 := \frac{3^8 - 0^0 - 2^2 - 2^9}{-3^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3023 := \frac{-3^1 + 0^1 - 2^9 + 3^8}{-3^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3024 := \frac{3^{11} + 0^0 + 2^2 + 4^7}{3^3 + 0^0 + 2^5 + 4^1}$$

$$3024 := \frac{3^{11} + 0^0 + 2^2 + 4^7}{3^3 + 0^0 + 2^5 + 4^1}$$

$$3025 := \frac{3^0 + 0^1 + 2^{10} + 5^9}{3^2 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 5^3}$$

$$3025 := \frac{3^0 + 0^1 + 2^{10} + 5^9}{3^2 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 5^3}$$

$$3026 := \frac{3^7 + 0^0 + 2^{13} + 6^5}{3^0 + 0^1 + 2^2 + 6^0}$$

$$3026 := \frac{3^7 + 0^0 + 2^{13} + 6^5}{3^0 + 0^1 + 2^2 + 6^0}$$

$$3027 := \frac{-3^7 + 0^1 + 2^{13} + 7^2}{-3^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3028 := \frac{3^3 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 8^5}{3^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 8^1}$$

$$3028 := \frac{3^3 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 8^5}{3^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 8^1}$$

$$3029 := \frac{3^{10} + 0^0 + 2^5 + 9^5}{3^3 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3029 := \frac{3^{10} + 0^0 + 2^5 + 9^5}{3^3 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3032 := \frac{-3^7 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 2^{17}}{-3^0 + 0^0 + 3^4 - 2^5}$$

$$3034 := \frac{3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6}{3^1 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 4^1}$$

$$3034 := \frac{3^8 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 4^6}{3^1 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 4^1}$$

$$3035 := \frac{-3^2 + 0^1 - 3^4 + 5^5}{-3^0 + 0^1 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3036 := \frac{3^7 + 0^1 + 3^{12} + 6^8}{-3^0 + 0^1 + 3^6 + 6^0}$$

$$3038 := \frac{3^3 + 0^1 + 3^8 - 8^3}{-3^0 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3042 := \frac{3^9 - 0^0 - 4^4 - 2^{14}}{-3^0 - 0^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3043 := \frac{3^3 + 0^1 + 4^{10} + 3^{10}}{3^3 + 0^1 + 4^4 + 3^4}$$

$$3043 := \frac{3^3 + 0^1 + 4^{10} + 3^{10}}{3^3 + 0^1 + 4^4 + 3^4}$$

$$3044 := \frac{-3^3 - 0^0 - 4^5 + 4^6}{-3^0 - 0^0 - 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3045 := \frac{-3^4 + 0^1 + 4^0 + 5^5}{-3^0 - 0^0 + 4^1 - 5^0}$$

$$3046 := \frac{3^7 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 6^7}{3^3 + 0^0 + 4^3 + 6^1}$$

$$3046 := \frac{3^7 + 0^0 + 4^7 + 6^7}{3^3 + 0^0 + 4^3 + 6^1}$$

$$3047 := \frac{3^{10} + 0^1 - 4^7 - 7^1}{3^1 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3048 := \frac{3^{10} - 0^0 - 4^7 + 8^1}{3^0 + 0^0 + 4^1 + 8^1}$$

$$3049 := \frac{3^7 + 0^1 - 4^4 + 9^5}{3^1 + 0^1 + 4^2 + 9^0}$$

$$3052 := \frac{3^3 + 0^1 + 5^8 + 2^2}{3^0 + 0^0 + 5^3 + 2^0}$$

$$3052 := \frac{3^3 + 0^1 + 5^8 + 2^2}{3^0 + 0^0 + 5^3 + 2^0}$$

$$3053 := \frac{3^2 + 0^1 + 5^5 - 3^4}{-3^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3054 := \frac{3^{10} + 0^1 + 5^7 + 4^4}{3^1 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 4^2}$$

$$3054 := \frac{3^{10} + 0^1 + 5^7 + 4^4}{3^1 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 4^2}$$

$$3055 := \frac{-3^{10} - 0^0 + 5^2 + 5^9}{-3^0 + 0^0 - 5^1 + 5^4}$$

$$3056 := \frac{3^{15} + 0^1 + 5^1 + 6^9}{3^5 - 0^0 - 5^2 + 6^5}$$

$$3057 := \frac{3^1 + 0^1 + 5^6 - 7^3}{3^1 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3058 := \frac{-3^1 + 0^1 + 5^5 - 8^2}{-3^0 - 0^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$3059 := \frac{3^9 - 0^0 + 5^7 + 9^2}{-3^0 - 0^0 + 5^2 + 9^1}$$

$$3062 := \frac{3^9 + 0^0 - 6^4 - 2^4}{3^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 2^2}$$

$$3063 := \frac{-3^2 + 0^1 - 6^4 + 3^9}{3^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$$

$$3064 := \frac{3^9 + 0^0 - 6^4 - 4^1}{3^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3065 := \frac{3^9 + 0^0 + 6^5 + 5^3}{3^0 + 0^0 + 6^1 + 5^0}$$

$$3065 := \frac{3^9 + 0^0 + 6^5 + 5^3}{3^0 + 0^0 + 6^1 + 5^0}$$

$$3066 := \frac{3^{13} - 0^0 - 6^0 - 6^0}{3^6 + 0^0 + 6^1 - 6^3}$$

$$3067 := \frac{-3^1 + 0^1 + 6^8 + 7^6}{3^3 + 0^3 + 6^3 + 7^3}$$

$$3068 := \frac{-3^6 + 0^0 - 6^6 + 8^6}{-3^0 + 0^0 + 6^1 + 8^2}$$

$$3069 := \frac{3^6 + 0^1 + 6^8 + 9^7}{3^4 + 0^1 + 6^4 + 9^3}$$

$$3069 := \frac{3^6 + 0^1 + 6^8 + 9^7}{3^4 + 0^1 + 6^4 + 9^3}$$

$$3072 := \frac{3^{10} + 0^1 + 7^3 + 2^{11}}{3^1 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 2^4}$$

$$3072 := \frac{3^{10} + 0^1 + 7^3 + 2^{11}}{3^1 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 2^4}$$

$$3073 := \frac{3^2 + 0^0 + 7^4 + 3^{10}}{3^1 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 3^2}$$

$$3073 := \frac{3^2 + 0^0 + 7^4 + 3^{10}}{3^1 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 3^2}$$

$$3074 := \frac{-3^8 + 0^1 + 7^5 - 4^5}{3^0 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3075 := \frac{3^{10} + 0^1 + 7^4 + 5^5}{3^2 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 5^1}$$

$$3075 := \frac{3^{10} + 0^1 + 7^4 + 5^5}{3^2 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 5^1}$$

$$3076 := \frac{3^{13} + 0^1 - 7^7 + 6^4}{3^3 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 6^3}$$

$$3077 := \frac{-3^6 - 0^0 + 7^1 + 7^6}{-3^1 - 0^0 - 7^1 + 7^2}$$

$$3078 := \frac{3^8 + 0^1 + 7^6 + 8^5}{3^0 + 0^1 + 7^2 + 8^0}$$

$$3078 := \frac{3^8 + 0^1 + 7^6 + 8^5}{3^0 + 0^1 + 7^2 + 8^0}$$

$$3079 := \frac{3^7 + 0^0 + 7^3 + 9^5}{3^1 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3079 := \frac{3^7 + 0^0 + 7^3 + 9^5}{3^1 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3081 := \frac{3^{10} + 0^0 - 8^3 + 1^0}{3^2 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3082 := \frac{3^7 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 2^{13}}{3^0 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3082 := \frac{3^7 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 2^{13}}{3^0 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3083 := \frac{-3^2 + 0^0 + 8^6 - 3^4}{3^1 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 3^4}$$

$$3084 := \frac{3^{10} - 0^0 + 8^3 - 4^7}{3^0 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 4^1}$$

$$3085 := \frac{3^9 - 0^0 + 8^5 - 5^1}{3^1 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$3086 := \frac{-3^7 - 0^0 - 8^1 + 6^7}{3^4 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 6^0}$$

$$3087 := \frac{3^{11} + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^0}{3^1 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 7^0}$$

$$3087 := \frac{3^{11} + 0^1 + 8^5 + 7^0}{3^1 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 7^0}$$

$$3089 := \frac{-3^9 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 9^3}{3^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3092 := \frac{3^7 + 0^1 + 9^5 + 2^{16}}{3^3 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3092 := \frac{3^7 + 0^1 + 9^5 + 2^{16}}{3^3 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3094 := \frac{3^6 - 0^0 + 9^6 - 4^0}{3^3 + 0^1 + 9^2 + 4^3}$$

$$3095 := \frac{-3^5 + 0^1 + 9^5 - 5^0}{3^2 + 0^1 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$3096 := \frac{-3^2 + 0^1 + 9^5 - 6^6}{3^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3097 := \frac{3^3 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 7^6}{3^3 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 7^0}$$

$$3097 := \frac{3^3 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 7^6}{3^3 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 7^0}$$

$$3104 := \frac{-3^8 + 1^0 + 0^1 + 4^8}{3^0 + 1^0 + 0^0 + 4^2}$$

$$3105 := \frac{-3^4 + 1^0 + 0^1 + 5^9}{3^1 + 1^0 + 0^1 + 5^4}$$

$$3106 := \frac{3^{10} + 1^0 + 0^1 - 6^2}{3^3 - 1^0 - 0^0 - 6^1}$$

$$3107 := \frac{3^{11} + 1^0 + 0^1 - 7^2}{3^2 - 1^0 + 0^1 + 7^2}$$

$$3108 := \frac{3^{10} + 1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0}{3^2 + 1^0 + 0^0 + 8^1}$$

$$3108 := \frac{3^{10} + 1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0}{3^2 + 1^0 + 0^0 + 8^1}$$

$$3120 := \frac{3^{13} - 1^0 - 2^0 - 0^0}{-3^0 - 1^0 + 2^9 + 0^0}$$

$$3121 := \frac{3^1 + 1^0 + 2^{16} + 1^0}{3^1 + 1^0 + 2^4 + 1^0}$$

$$3121 := \frac{3^1 + 1^0 + 2^{16} + 1^0}{3^1 + 1^0 + 2^4 + 1^0}$$

$$3122 := \frac{3^2 + 1^0 + 2^4 + 2^{16}}{3^1 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 2^4}$$

$$3122 := \frac{3^2 + 1^0 + 2^4 + 2^{16}}{3^1 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 2^4}$$

$$3123 := \frac{-3^5 - 1^0 + 2^{12} - 3^6}{-3^0 - 1^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$3124 := \frac{3^1 + 1^0 + 2^6 + 4^8}{3^1 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 4^2}$$

$$3124 := \frac{3^1 + 1^0 + 2^6 + 4^8}{3^1 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 4^2}$$

$$3125 := \frac{-3^0 - 1^0 + 2^1 + 5^5}{-3^0 - 1^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$3126 := \frac{3^{10} + 1^0 + 2^7 + 6^3}{3^0 + 1^0 + 2^4 + 6^0}$$

$$3126 := \frac{3^{10} + 1^0 + 2^7 + 6^3}{3^0 + 1^0 + 2^4 + 6^0}$$

$$3127 := \frac{3^4 + 1^0 + 2^{16} + 7^2}{3^1 + 1^0 + 2^4 + 7^0}$$

$$3127 := \frac{3^4 + 1^0 + 2^{16} + 7^2}{3^1 + 1^0 + 2^4 + 7^0}$$

$$3128 := \frac{3^{10} - 1^0 - 2^7 + 8^3}{3^0 + 1^0 + 2^4 + 8^0}$$

$$3129 := \frac{3^7 - 1^0 + 2^{10} - 9^2}{-3^0 - 1^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3139 := \frac{3^0 + 1^0 + 3^7 + 9^6}{3^2 - 1^0 + 3^4 + 9^2}$$

$$3142 := \frac{3^7 - 1^0 + 4^6 + 2^1}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3143 := \frac{-3^9 - 1^0 + 4^1 + 3^{13}}{3^0 + 1^0 + 4^4 + 3^5}$$

$$3144 := \frac{3^7 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 4^6}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3145 := \frac{3^5 + 1^0 + 4^4 + 5^7}{3^1 + 1^0 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$3146 := \frac{-3^1 - 1^0 + 4^8 - 6^6}{3^1 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3147 := \frac{3^3 + 1^0 + 4^9 + 7^7}{3^4 + 1^0 + 4^4 + 7^1}$$

$$3148 := \frac{3^7 + 1^0 + 4^5 - 8^2}{-3^0 - 1^0 + 4^1 - 8^0}$$

$$3149 := \frac{-3^5 + 1^0 + 4^5 + 9^5}{3^0 + 1^0 + 4^2 + 9^0}$$

$$3150 := \frac{3^3 - 1^0 + 5^5 - 0^0}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3152 := \frac{3^3 - 1^0 + 5^5 + 2^0}{-3^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3153 := \frac{-3^0 - 1^0 + 5^9 + 3^{12}}{3^4 + 1^4 + 5^4 + 3^4}$$

$$3154 := \frac{3^3 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 4^0}{-3^0 - 1^0 - 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3155 := \frac{3^8 - 1^0 - 5^3 - 5^3}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3159 := \frac{-3^5 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 9^4}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3162 := \frac{-3^0 - 1^0 + 6^4 + 2^{13}}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3163 := \frac{-3^1 - 1^0 - 6^5 + 3^{16}}{-3^6 - 1^0 + 6^5 + 3^8}$$

$$3164 := \frac{3^8 - 1^0 - 6^3 - 4^2}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3165 := \frac{3^9 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 5^3}{3^2 + 1^0 + 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$3166 := \frac{3^{11} + 1^0 - 6^4 + 6^5}{3^3 + 1^0 - 6^1 + 6^2}$$

$$3167 := \frac{3^6 + 1^0 + 6^2 + 7^4}{-3^0 + 1^0 - 6^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3168 := \frac{3^8 - 1^0 - 6^3 - 8^1}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3169 := \frac{3^7 - 1^0 + 6^7 - 9^2}{3^0 + 1^0 + 6^1 + 9^2}$$

$$3173 := \frac{3^7 - 1^0 - 7^4 + 3^8}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3174 := \frac{-3^8 + 1^0 + 7^6 + 4^0}{3^0 + 1^0 + 7^2 - 4^2}$$

$$3175 := \frac{3^9 - 1^0 - 7^1 - 5^4}{3^1 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3179 := \frac{3^7 - 1^0 + 7^5 + 9^2}{3^1 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3182 := \frac{-3^8 + 1^0 + 8^6 - 2^{10}}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 8^2 + 2^4}$$

$$3183 := \frac{-3^{12} + 1^0 - 8^2 + 3^{15}}{3^0 + 1^0 + 8^4 + 3^5}$$

$$3184 := \frac{3^8 - 1^0 + 8^2 - 4^4}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3185 := \frac{-3^1 - 1^0 + 8^2 + 5^5}{-3^0 - 1^0 + 8^1 - 5^1}$$

$$3186 := \frac{3^{11} - 1^0 - 8^3 - 6^5}{-3^2 - 1^0 + 8^2 - 6^0}$$

$$3187 := \frac{-3^3 + 1^0 + 8^5 - 7^5}{-3^0 - 1^0 + 8^1 - 7^0}$$

$$3189 := \frac{-3^7 - 1^0 + 8^6 - 9^5}{-3^0 - 1^0 + 8^2 + 9^0}$$

$$3195 := \frac{-3^{11} + 1^0 + 9^6 - 5^6}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 9^2 + 5^2}$$

$$3199 := \frac{-3^4 - 1^0 - 9^2 + 9^4}{-3^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3202 := \frac{3^{10} + 2^0 + 0^1 + 2^{13}}{3^0 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 2^4}$$

$$3202 := \frac{3^{10} + 2^0 + 0^1 + 2^{13}}{3^0 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 2^4}$$

$$3203 := \frac{3^0 + 2^8 + 0^1 + 3^{12}}{3^4 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 3^4}$$

$$3203 := \frac{3^0 + 2^8 + 0^1 + 3^{12}}{3^4 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 3^4}$$

$$3204 := \frac{3^7 - 2^3 + 0^0 + 4^5}{-3^0 - 2^0 - 0^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3205 := \frac{3^4 - 2^0 + 0^1 + 5^5}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$3206 := \frac{3^7 + 2^2 + 0^0 + 6^7}{3^4 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3206 := \frac{3^7 + 2^2 + 0^0 + 6^7}{3^4 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3207 := \frac{3^{15} + 2^4 + 0^0 + 7^4}{3^3 + 2^{11} - 0^0 + 7^4}$$

$$3208 := \frac{3^{12} + 2^{10} - 0^0 + 8^2}{-3^3 + 2^7 + 0^0 + 8^2}$$

$$3209 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{10} - 0^0 - 9^0}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3210 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{10} - 1^0 + 0^1}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3211 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{10} - 1^0 + 1^0}{3^0 - 2^1 + 1^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3212 := \frac{3^7 + 2^9 + 1^0 + 2^9}{-3^0 - 2^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3213 := \frac{3^0 + 2^{10} + 1^0 + 3^7}{3^0 - 2^1 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3214 := \frac{3^7 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 4^5}{-3^0 - 2^0 - 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3215 := \frac{3^4 + 2^3 + 1^0 + 5^5}{3^0 - 2^1 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3216 := \frac{3^{10} + 2^{11} + 1^0 + 6^1}{3^0 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3216 := \frac{3^{10} + 2^{11} + 1^0 + 6^1}{3^0 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3217 := \frac{3^4 + 2^{19} + 1^0 + 7^0}{3^3 + 2^7 + 1^0 + 7^1}$$

$$3217 := \frac{3^4 + 2^{19} + 1^0 + 7^0}{3^3 + 2^7 + 1^0 + 7^1}$$

$$3218 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{10} - 1^0 + 8^1}{3^0 - 2^1 + 1^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3219 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{10} - 1^0 + 9^1}{3^0 - 2^1 + 1^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3220 := \frac{3^7 + 2^3 + 2^{10} + 0^0}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3221 := \frac{3^8 + 2^3 - 2^7 + 1^0}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3222 := \frac{-3^5 + 2^0 - 2^5 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3223 := \frac{3^8 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 3^{11}}{3^3 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 3^3}$$

$$3223 := \frac{3^8 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 3^{11}}{3^3 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 3^3}$$

$$3224 := \frac{3^8 - 2^0 - 2^7 + 4^2}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3225 := \frac{3^5 + 2^0 + 2^8 + 5^6}{3^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$3225 := \frac{3^5 + 2^0 + 2^8 + 5^6}{3^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$3226 := \frac{3^{13} + 2^{12} + 2^{19} + 6^0}{3^4 + 2^6 + 2^9 + 6^0}$$

$$3226 := \frac{3^{13} + 2^{12} + 2^{19} + 6^0}{3^4 + 2^6 + 2^9 + 6^0}$$

$$3227 := \frac{3^7 + 2^7 + 2^{13} + 7^4}{3^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3227 := \frac{3^7 + 2^7 + 2^{13} + 7^4}{3^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3228 := \frac{3^7 + 2^0 + 2^{16} + 8^2}{3^0 + 2^2 + 2^3 + 8^1}$$

$$3228 := \frac{3^7 + 2^0 + 2^{16} + 8^2}{3^0 + 2^2 + 2^3 + 8^1}$$

$$3229 := \frac{3^{11} + 2^7 + 2^{14} + 9^2}{3^1 + 2^4 + 2^5 + 9^1}$$

$$3229 := \frac{3^{11} + 2^7 + 2^{14} + 9^2}{3^1 + 2^4 + 2^5 + 9^1}$$

$$3230 := \frac{3^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 0^1}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 0^0}$$

$$3231 := \frac{3^8 + 2^{15} + 3^{11} + 1^0}{3^0 + 2^6 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3231 := \frac{3^8 + 2^{15} + 3^{11} + 1^0}{3^0 + 2^6 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3232 := \frac{3^8 + 2^2 + 3^{11} + 2^9}{3^3 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 2^1}$$

$$3232 := \frac{3^8 + 2^2 + 3^{11} + 2^9}{3^3 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 2^1}$$

$$3233 := \frac{3^6 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 3^9}{3^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 3^1}$$

$$3233 := \frac{3^6 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 3^9}{3^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 3^1}$$

$$3234 := \frac{3^5 + 2^{11} + 3^6 + 4^7}{3^0 + 2^0 + 3^1 + 4^0}$$

$$3234 := \frac{3^5 + 2^{11} + 3^6 + 4^7}{3^0 + 2^0 + 3^1 + 4^0}$$

$$3235 := \frac{3^5 + 2^6 + 3^5 + 5^6}{3^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3236 := \frac{3^7 + 2^5 + 3^{10} + 6^3}{3^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 6^0}$$

$$3236 := \frac{3^7 + 2^5 + 3^{10} + 6^3}{3^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 6^0}$$

$$3237 := \frac{3^6 + 2^{13} + 3^{10} + 7^1}{3^0 + 2^2 + 3^2 + 7^1}$$

$$3238 := \frac{3^4 + 2^2 + 3^{11} + 8^4}{3^3 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 8^0}$$

$$3239 := \frac{3^9 + 2^1 + 3^{11} + 9^5}{3^1 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3239 := \frac{3^9 + 2^1 + 3^{11} + 9^5}{3^1 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3240 := \frac{-3^6 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 0^0}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3241 := \frac{3^8 - 2^4 - 4^3 + 1^0}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3242 := \frac{3^7 - 2^0 + 4^5 + 2^5}{-3^0 - 2^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3243 := \frac{3^7 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 3^8}{3^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3243 := \frac{3^7 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 3^8}{3^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3244 := \frac{3^7 + 2^5 + 4^0 + 4^5}{-3^0 - 2^0 - 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3245 := \frac{3^{10} + 2^{13} + 4^5 + 5^5}{3^0 + 2^2 + 4^2 + 5^0}$$

$$3245 := \frac{3^{10} + 2^{13} + 4^5 + 5^5}{3^0 + 2^2 + 4^2 + 5^0}$$

$$3246 := \frac{3^6 + 2^{17} + 4^0 + 6^5}{3^0 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 6^2}$$

$$3246 := \frac{3^6 + 2^{17} + 4^0 + 6^5}{3^0 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 6^2}$$

$$3247 := \frac{3^{12} + 2^7 + 4^8 + 7^3}{3^1 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^2}$$

$$3247 := \frac{3^{12} + 2^7 + 4^8 + 7^3}{3^1 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^2}$$

$$3248 := \frac{3^8 - 2^1 + 4^0 - 8^2}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3249 := \frac{3^5 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 9^6}{3^1 + 2^4 + 4^3 + 9^2}$$

$$3249 := \frac{3^5 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 9^6}{3^1 + 2^4 + 4^3 + 9^2}$$

$$3250 := \frac{3^8 + 2^6 + 5^5 + 0^1}{3^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3250 := \frac{3^8 + 2^6 + 5^5 + 0^1}{3^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3251 := \frac{3^{11} + 2^{17} + 5^4 + 1^0}{3^4 + 2^3 + 5^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3251 := \frac{3^{11} + 2^{17} + 5^4 + 1^0}{3^4 + 2^3 + 5^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3252 := \frac{3^0 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3252 := \frac{3^0 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3253 := \frac{3^4 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 3^{10}}{3^0 + 2^3 + 5^1 + 3^2}$$

$$3253 := \frac{3^4 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 3^{10}}{3^0 + 2^3 + 5^1 + 3^2}$$

$$3254 := \frac{3^{11} + 2^{13} + 5^2 + 4^7}{3^0 + 2^5 + 5^2 + 4^1}$$

$$3255 := \frac{3^2 + 2^4 + 5^4 + 5^6}{3^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3256 := \frac{3^7 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 6^6}{3^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3256 := \frac{3^7 + 2^7 + 5^5 + 6^6}{3^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3257 := \frac{3^9 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 7^1}{3^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 7^1}$$

$$3258 := \frac{3^0 + 2^1 + 5^7 + 8^2}{3^1 + 2^3 + 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$3258 := \frac{3^0 + 2^1 + 5^7 + 8^2}{3^1 + 2^3 + 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$3259 := \frac{3^9 + 2^2 + 5^5 + 9^0}{3^0 + 2^2 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3259 := \frac{3^9 + 2^2 + 5^5 + 9^0}{3^0 + 2^2 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3260 := \frac{3^8 - 2^2 - 6^2 - 0^0}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 0^0}$$

$$3261 := \frac{3^8 - 2^1 - 6^2 - 1^0}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3262 := \frac{3^1 + 2^0 + 6^7 + 2^{17}}{3^4 + 2^0 + 6^2 + 2^3}$$

$$3262 := \frac{3^1 + 2^0 + 6^7 + 2^{17}}{3^4 + 2^0 + 6^2 + 2^3}$$

$$3263 := \frac{3^6 + 2^{13} + 6^4 + 3^{12}}{3^0 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 3^0}$$

$$3263 := \frac{3^6 + 2^{13} + 6^4 + 3^{12}}{3^0 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 3^0}$$

$$3264 := \frac{-3^4 + 2^{11} + 6^4 + 4^0}{-3^0 - 2^0 - 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3265 := \frac{3^1 + 2^4 + 6^3 + 5^7}{3^0 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 5^0}$$

$$3265 := \frac{3^1 + 2^4 + 6^3 + 5^7}{3^0 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 5^0}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 3266 := \frac{3^7 - 2^0 - 6^3 + 6^4}{3^0 - 2^1 + 6^0 + 6^0} & 3276 := \frac{3^4 + 2^1 + 7^4 + 6^6}{3^0 + 2^0 + 7^1 + 6^1} & 3285 := \frac{3^9 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 5^2}{3^1 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 5^0} \\
 3267 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{17} + 6^3 + 7^5}{3^0 + 2^1 + 6^2 + 7^1} & 3277 := \frac{3^9 + 2^9 + 7^3 + 7^4}{3^0 + 2^2 + 7^0 + 7^0} & 3286 := \frac{3^2 + 2^{14} + 8^0 + 6^2}{3^0 + 2^1 + 8^0 + 6^0} \\
 3267 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{17} + 6^3 + 7^5}{3^0 + 2^1 + 6^2 + 7^1} & 3277 := \frac{3^9 + 2^9 + 7^3 + 7^4}{3^0 + 2^2 + 7^0 + 7^0} & 3286 := \frac{3^2 + 2^{14} + 8^0 + 6^2}{3^0 + 2^1 + 8^0 + 6^0} \\
 3268 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{16} + 6^6 + 8^0}{3^0 + 2^5 + 6^0 + 8^0} & 3278 := \frac{3^0 + 2^2 + 7^1 + 8^5}{3^0 + 2^0 + 7^1 + 8^0} & 3287 := \frac{3^0 + 2^{14} + 8^0 + 7^2}{3^0 + 2^1 + 8^0 + 7^0} \\
 3268 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{16} + 6^6 + 8^0}{3^0 + 2^5 + 6^0 + 8^0} & 3278 := \frac{3^0 + 2^2 + 7^1 + 8^5}{3^0 + 2^0 + 7^1 + 8^0} & 3287 := \frac{3^0 + 2^{14} + 8^0 + 7^2}{3^0 + 2^1 + 8^0 + 7^0} \\
 3269 := \frac{3^{13} + 2^2 + 6^3 + 9^3}{3^5 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 9^2} & 3279 := \frac{3^0 + 2^{14} + 7^0 + 9^1}{3^0 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 9^0} & 3288 := \frac{3^6 + 2^{11} - 8^0 + 8^3}{3^0 - 2^1 + 8^0 + 8^0} \\
 3269 := \frac{3^{13} + 2^2 + 6^3 + 9^3}{3^5 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 9^2} & 3279 := \frac{3^0 + 2^{14} + 7^0 + 9^1}{3^0 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 9^0} & 3289 := \frac{3^4 + 2^3 + 8^2 + 9^5}{3^0 + 2^3 + 8^1 + 9^0} \\
 3270 := \frac{3^9 + 2^3 + 7^6 + 0^1}{3^1 + 2^5 + 7^1 + 0^1} & 3280 := \frac{3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0}{3^0 + 2^0 + 8^1 + 0^1} & 3289 := \frac{3^4 + 2^3 + 8^2 + 9^5}{3^0 + 2^3 + 8^1 + 9^0} \\
 3270 := \frac{3^9 + 2^3 + 7^6 + 0^1}{3^1 + 2^5 + 7^1 + 0^1} & 3280 := \frac{3^3 + 2^2 + 8^5 + 0^0}{3^0 + 2^0 + 8^1 + 0^1} & 3290 := \frac{3^9 - 2^{14} - 9^1 + 0^1}{-3^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 0^1} \\
 3271 := \frac{-3^3 + 2^{14} - 7^0 - 1^0}{3^0 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 1^0} & 3281 := \frac{3^9 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 1^0}{3^1 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 1^0} & 3291 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{10} + 9^2 - 1^0}{3^0 - 2^1 + 9^0 + 1^0} \\
 3272 := \frac{3^6 + 2^{11} + 7^5 + 2^{15}}{3^0 + 2^2 + 7^1 + 2^2} & 3281 := \frac{3^9 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 1^0}{3^1 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 1^0} & 3292 := \frac{3^1 + 2^6 + 9^1 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 2^1} \\
 3272 := \frac{3^6 + 2^{11} + 7^5 + 2^{15}}{3^0 + 2^2 + 7^1 + 2^2} & 3282 := \frac{3^2 + 2^4 + 8^0 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 2^1} & 3293 := \frac{3^3 + 2^{14} + 9^3 + 3^{11}}{3^2 + 2^5 + 9^1 + 3^2} \\
 3273 := \frac{3^6 + 2^3 + 7^4 + 3^{10}}{3^0 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 3^2} & 3282 := \frac{3^2 + 2^4 + 8^0 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 2^1} & 3293 := \frac{3^3 + 2^{14} + 9^3 + 3^{11}}{3^2 + 2^5 + 9^1 + 3^2} \\
 3273 := \frac{3^6 + 2^3 + 7^4 + 3^{10}}{3^0 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 3^2} & 3283 := \frac{3^8 + 2^1 + 8^1 + 3^8}{3^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 3^0} & 3294 := \frac{3^0 + 2^2 + 9^2 + 4^7}{3^0 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 4^0} \\
 3274 := \frac{3^7 + 2^{10} + 7^2 + 4^7}{3^1 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 4^0} & 3283 := \frac{3^8 + 2^1 + 8^1 + 3^8}{3^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 3^0} & 3295 := \frac{3^2 + 2^{14} + 9^2 + 5^0}{3^0 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 5^0} \\
 3275 := \frac{3^{10} + 2^1 + 7^2 + 5^5}{3^0 + 2^4 + 7^0 + 5^0} & 3284 := \frac{3^1 + 2^5 + 8^0 + 4^7}{3^0 + 2^1 + 8^0 + 4^0} & 3296 := \frac{3^2 + 2^{14} + 9^2 + 6^1}{3^0 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 6^0} \\
 3275 := \frac{3^{10} + 2^1 + 7^2 + 5^5}{3^0 + 2^4 + 7^0 + 5^0} & 3284 := \frac{3^1 + 2^5 + 8^0 + 4^7}{3^0 + 2^1 + 8^0 + 4^0} & 3296 := \frac{3^2 + 2^{14} + 9^2 + 6^1}{3^0 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 6^0} \\
 3276 := \frac{3^4 + 2^1 + 7^4 + 6^6}{3^0 + 2^0 + 7^1 + 6^1} & 3285 := \frac{3^9 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 5^2}{3^1 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 5^0} & 3297 := \frac{3^0 + 2^{16} + 9^2 + 7^5}{3^0 + 2^3 + 9^1 + 7^1}
 \end{array}$$

$$3297 := \frac{3^0 + 2^{16} + 9^2 + 7^5}{3^0 + 2^3 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3298 := \frac{3^9 + 2^4 + 9^2 + 8^1}{3^1 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3298 := \frac{3^9 + 2^4 + 9^2 + 8^1}{3^1 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3299 := \frac{3^3 + 2^2 + 9^5 + 9^6}{3^0 + 2^4 + 9^2 + 9^2}$$

$$3299 := \frac{3^3 + 2^2 + 9^5 + 9^6}{3^0 + 2^4 + 9^2 + 9^2}$$

$$3302 := \frac{3^0 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 2^7}{3^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3302 := \frac{3^0 + 3^9 + 0^1 + 2^7}{3^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3305 := \frac{3^4 - 3^8 + 0^1 + 5^9}{-3^2 - 3^3 + 0^1 + 5^4}$$

$$3306 := \frac{3^5 + 3^{10} + 0^1 + 6^3}{3^1 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3306 := \frac{3^5 + 3^{10} + 0^1 + 6^3}{3^1 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3307 := \frac{3^1 + 3^8 + 0^0 + 7^2}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3308 := \frac{-3^2 + 3^8 + 0^1 + 8^2}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3315 := \frac{3^4 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 5^3}{3^0 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3315 := \frac{3^4 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 5^3}{3^0 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3317 := \frac{3^4 + 3^8 - 1^0 - 7^1}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3319 := \frac{-3^1 + 3^4 - 1^0 + 9^4}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3320 := \frac{3^4 + 3^8 - 2^0 - 0^0}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 0^0}$$

$$3321 := \frac{3^4 + 3^8 - 2^0 + 1^0}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3322 := \frac{3^4 + 3^4 + 2^6 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3322 := \frac{3^4 + 3^4 + 2^6 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3323 := \frac{3^5 + 3^5 + 2^{14} + 3^9}{3^1 + 3^1 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$3323 := \frac{3^5 + 3^5 + 2^{14} + 3^9}{3^1 + 3^1 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$3324 := \frac{3^3 + 3^4 + 2^7 + 4^7}{3^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 4^0}$$

$$3325 := \frac{3^5 + 3^9 + 2^{10} + 5^6}{3^0 + 3^0 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$3326 := \frac{3^1 + 3^3 + 2^{14} + 6^3}{3^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$3326 := \frac{3^1 + 3^3 + 2^{14} + 6^3}{3^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$3327 := \frac{3^0 + 3^5 + 2^{14} + 7^1}{3^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$3327 := \frac{3^0 + 3^5 + 2^{14} + 7^1}{3^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$3328 := \frac{3^0 + 3^{11} + 2^2 + 8^6}{3^0 + 3^1 + 2^6 + 8^2}$$

$$3328 := \frac{3^0 + 3^{11} + 2^2 + 8^6}{3^0 + 3^1 + 2^6 + 8^2}$$

$$3329 := \frac{3^2 + 3^5 + 2^{14} + 9^1}{3^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3329 := \frac{3^2 + 3^5 + 2^{14} + 9^1}{3^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3331 := \frac{3^4 - 3^7 + 3^{13} + 1^0}{-3^2 + 3^5 + 3^5 + 1^0}$$

$$3332 := \frac{-3^5 + 3^9 + 3^{11} + 2^0}{3^0 + 3^3 + 3^3 + 2^2}$$

$$3333 := \frac{-3^1 + 3^3 + 3^4 + 3^8}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3334 := \frac{3^3 + 3^4 + 3^8 - 4^0}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3335 := \frac{3^1 + 3^4 + 3^8 + 5^2}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3337 := \frac{3^5 + 3^7 + 3^{12} + 7^2}{3^1 + 3^3 + 3^4 + 7^2}$$

$$3337 := \frac{3^5 + 3^7 + 3^{12} + 7^2}{3^1 + 3^3 + 3^4 + 7^2}$$

$$3338 := \frac{3^7 + 3^7 + 3^{10} - 8^0}{3^0 + 3^0 + 3^2 + 8^1}$$

$$3339 := \frac{3^3 + 3^5 + 3^9 + 9^2}{3^0 + 3^0 + 3^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3339 := \frac{3^3 + 3^5 + 3^9 + 9^2}{3^0 + 3^0 + 3^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3340 := \frac{-3^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 0^1}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3341 := \frac{-3^3 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 1^0}{-3^0 - 3^0 + 4^1 - 1^0}$$

$$3342 := \frac{3^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 2^1}{3^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3343 := \frac{3^0 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 3^{11}}{3^0 + 3^2 + 4^2 + 3^3}$$

$$3343 := \frac{3^0 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 3^{11}}{3^0 + 3^2 + 4^2 + 3^3}$$

$$3344 := \frac{-3^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 4^6}{-3^0 - 3^0 - 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3345 := \frac{3^2 + 3^{11} + 4^1 + 5^3}{3^1 + 3^2 + 4^2 + 5^2}$$

$$3346 := \frac{3^8 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^1}{3^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3346 := \frac{3^8 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^1}{3^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3347 := \frac{3^9 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 7^2}{3^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3347 := \frac{3^9 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 7^2}{3^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3348 := \frac{3^1 + 3^{10} + 4^8 + 8^5}{3^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 8^0}$$

$$3348 := \frac{3^1 + 3^{10} + 4^8 + 8^5}{3^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 8^0}$$

$$3349 := \frac{3^5 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 9^5}{3^1 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3349 := \frac{3^5 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 9^5}{3^1 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3351 := \frac{-3^4 - 3^6 + 5^{10} - 1^0}{3^6 + 3^7 - 5^0 - 1^0}$$

$$3352 := \frac{-3^5 + 3^{15} + 5^{10} - 2^0}{3^2 + 3^8 + 5^4 - 2^0}$$

$$3353 := \frac{3^0 + 3^3 + 5^8 + 3^{13}}{3^4 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 3^5}$$

$$3353 := \frac{3^0 + 3^3 + 5^8 + 3^{13}}{3^4 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 3^5}$$

$$3354 := \frac{-3^4 + 3^8 - 5^5 - 4^0}{-3^0 - 3^0 - 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3355 := \frac{3^1 + 3^{11} + 5^8 + 5^{10}}{3^5 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 5^4}$$

$$3355 := \frac{3^1 + 3^{11} + 5^8 + 5^{10}}{3^5 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 5^4}$$

$$3356 := \frac{-3^4 + 3^8 - 5^5 + 6^0}{-3^0 + 3^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3357 := \frac{3^0 + 3^4 + 5^6 + 7^7}{3^0 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 7^0}$$

$$3357 := \frac{3^0 + 3^4 + 5^6 + 7^7}{3^0 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 7^0}$$

$$3358 := \frac{-3^2 + 3^5 + 5^5 - 8^0}{-3^0 - 3^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$3359 := \frac{3^1 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 9^4}{3^0 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3359 := \frac{3^1 + 3^9 + 5^4 + 9^4}{3^0 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3360 := \frac{3^{13} + 3^{13} - 6^1 + 0^1}{3^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 0^0}$$

$$3361 := \frac{-3^5 - 3^6 + 6^7 - 1^0}{-3^1 + 3^4 + 6^1 - 1^0}$$

$$3362 := \frac{3^7 + 3^9 + 6^1 + 2^{16}}{3^0 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 2^4}$$

$$3362 := \frac{3^7 + 3^9 + 6^1 + 2^{16}}{3^0 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 2^4}$$

$$3363 := \frac{3^5 + 3^5 + 6^9 + 3^6}{3^5 + 3^6 + 6^4 + 3^6}$$

$$3363 := \frac{3^5 + 3^5 + 6^9 + 3^6}{3^5 + 3^6 + 6^4 + 3^6}$$

$$3364 := \frac{3^4 + 3^{11} + 6^5 + 4^2}{3^2 + 3^2 + 6^2 + 4^0}$$

$$3364 := \frac{3^4 + 3^{11} + 6^5 + 4^2}{3^2 + 3^2 + 6^2 + 4^0}$$

$$3365 := \frac{3^3 + 3^{11} + 6^5 + 5^3}{3^2 + 3^2 + 6^2 + 5^0}$$

$$3365 := \frac{3^3 + 3^{11} + 6^5 + 5^3}{3^2 + 3^2 + 6^2 + 5^0}$$

$$3366 := \frac{3^4 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 6^3}{3^0 + 3^1 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3366 := \frac{3^4 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 6^3}{3^0 + 3^1 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3367 := \frac{3^0 + 3^{11} + 6^4 + 7^1}{3^0 + 3^2 + 6^2 + 7^1}$$

$$3367 := \frac{3^0 + 3^{11} + 6^4 + 7^1}{3^0 + 3^2 + 6^2 + 7^1}$$

$$3368 := \frac{3^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 8^6}{3^0 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 8^2}$$

$$3368 := \frac{3^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 8^6}{3^0 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 8^2}$$

$$3369 := \frac{3^6 + 3^8 + 6^7 + 9^6}{3^2 + 3^2 + 6^3 + 9^1}$$

$$3369 := \frac{3^6 + 3^8 + 6^7 + 9^6}{3^2 + 3^2 + 6^3 + 9^1}$$

$$3370 := \frac{-3^4 + 3^7 + 7^7 + 0^0}{3^0 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3372 := \frac{3^5 + 3^6 + 7^4 - 2^0}{-3^0 - 3^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3373 := \frac{3^3 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 3^8}{3^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3373 := \frac{3^3 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 3^8}{3^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3374 := \frac{3^5 + 3^6 + 7^4 + 4^0}{-3^0 - 3^0 - 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3375 := \frac{3^9 + 3^{12} + 7^0 + 5^9}{3^0 + 3^6 + 7^1 + 5^1}$$

$$3375 := \frac{3^9 + 3^{12} + 7^0 + 5^9}{3^0 + 3^6 + 7^1 + 5^1}$$

$$3376 := \frac{-3^2 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^0}{-3^0 - 3^0 + 7^0 + 6^1}$$

$$3377 := \frac{3^5 + 3^8 - 7^0 - 7^2}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3378 := \frac{3^5 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^0}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3379 := \frac{3^1 + 3^5 - 7^2 + 9^4}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3381 := \frac{3^0 + 3^{10} + 8^6 + 1^0}{3^1 + 3^3 + 8^2 + 1^0}$$

$$3381 := \frac{3^0 + 3^{10} + 8^6 + 1^0}{3^1 + 3^3 + 8^2 + 1^0}$$

$$3382 := \frac{3^4 + 3^9 + 8^3 + 2^4}{3^0 + 3^1 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3382 := \frac{3^4 + 3^9 + 8^3 + 2^4}{3^0 + 3^1 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3383 := \frac{3^5 + 3^{10} + 8^2 + 3^{10}}{3^2 + 3^2 + 8^1 + 3^2}$$

$$3383 := \frac{3^5 + 3^{10} + 8^2 + 3^{10}}{3^2 + 3^2 + 8^1 + 3^2}$$

$$3384 := \frac{3^0 - 3^6 + 8^4 + 4^2}{-3^0 - 3^0 - 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3385 := \frac{3^0 + 3^9 + 8^0 + 5^4}{3^0 + 3^1 + 8^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3386 := \frac{3^6 + 3^{11} + 8^6 + 6^8}{3^3 + 3^4 + 8^3 + 6^1}$$

$$3386 := \frac{3^6 + 3^{11} + 8^6 + 6^8}{3^3 + 3^4 + 8^3 + 6^1}$$

$$3387 := \frac{3^9 + 3^{11} + 8^3 + 7^6}{3^0 + 3^3 + 8^2 + 7^0}$$

$$3387 := \frac{3^9 + 3^{11} + 8^3 + 7^6}{3^0 + 3^3 + 8^2 + 7^0}$$

$$3388 := \frac{3^7 + 3^8 + 8^4 + 8^4}{-3^0 - 3^0 - 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$3389 := \frac{-3^3 + 3^5 + 8^0 + 9^4}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3393 := \frac{-3^2 - 3^2 + 9^4 + 3^5}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3395 := \frac{3^9 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 5^7}{3^2 + 3^2 + 9^1 + 5^2}$$

$$3395 := \frac{3^9 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 5^7}{3^2 + 3^2 + 9^1 + 5^2}$$

$$3397 := \frac{-3^1 + 3^5 + 9^4 - 7^1}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3398 := \frac{-3^2 + 3^5 + 9^4 + 8^0}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3399 := \frac{3^1 + 3^5 - 9^1 + 9^4}{-3^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3402 := \frac{3^7 + 4^5 + 0^0 + 2^{18}}{3^2 + 4^1 + 0^0 + 2^6}$$

$$3402 := \frac{3^7 + 4^5 + 0^0 + 2^{18}}{3^2 + 4^1 + 0^0 + 2^6}$$

$$3403 := \frac{3^7 + 4^5 + 0^0 + 3^{11}}{3^2 + 4^2 + 0^0 + 3^3}$$

$$3403 := \frac{3^7 + 4^5 + 0^0 + 3^{11}}{3^2 + 4^2 + 0^0 + 3^3}$$

$$3404 := \frac{3^3 - 4^3 + 0^0 + 4^9}{3^2 + 4^1 + 0^1 + 4^3}$$

$$3405 := \frac{3^{10} + 4^8 + 0^1 - 5^6}{3^1 + 4^1 + 0^1 + 5^2}$$

$$3406 := \frac{3^1 + 4^5 + 0^0 + 6^6}{3^1 + 4^1 + 0^0 + 6^1}$$

$$3406 := \frac{3^1 + 4^5 + 0^0 + 6^6}{3^1 + 4^1 + 0^0 + 6^1}$$

$$3407 := \frac{3^{11} + 4^2 + 0^1 + 7^0}{3^0 + 4^0 + 0^0 + 7^2}$$

$$3407 := \frac{3^{11} + 4^2 + 0^1 + 7^0}{3^0 + 4^0 + 0^0 + 7^2}$$

$$3408 := \frac{3^{11} + 4^1 + 0^0 + 8^2}{3^3 + 4^2 + 0^0 + 8^1}$$

$$3408 := \frac{3^{11} + 4^1 + 0^0 + 8^2}{3^3 + 4^2 + 0^0 + 8^1}$$

$$3409 := \frac{3^0 + 4^4 + 0^1 + 9^4}{-3^0 + 4^0 + 0^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3411 := \frac{-3^6 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 1^0}{3^0 + 4^2 + 1^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3412 := \frac{3^9 + 4^9 + 1^0 + 2^{13}}{3^4 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3412 := \frac{3^9 + 4^9 + 1^0 + 2^{13}}{3^4 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3413 := \frac{-3^1 - 4^5 - 1^0 + 3^{10}}{3^1 + 4^1 + 1^0 + 3^2}$$

$$3414 := \frac{3^1 + 4^6 + 1^0 + 4^7}{3^1 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3414 := \frac{3^1 + 4^6 + 1^0 + 4^7}{3^1 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3415 := \frac{3^9 + 4^6 + 1^0 + 5^3}{3^0 + 4^1 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3415 := \frac{3^9 + 4^6 + 1^0 + 5^3}{3^0 + 4^1 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3416 := \frac{3^4 - 4^5 - 1^0 + 6^5}{-3^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3417 := \frac{-3^2 + 4^5 + 1^0 + 7^4}{-3^0 + 4^1 - 1^0 - 7^0}$$

$$3418 := \frac{3^3 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 8^4}{3^1 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3418 := \frac{3^3 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 8^4}{3^1 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3419 := \frac{3^4 + 4^{11} - 1^0 + 9^3}{3^5 + 4^4 - 1^0 + 9^3}$$

$$3420 := \frac{3^7 + 4^6 + 2^{16} + 0^0}{3^0 + 4^1 + 2^4 + 0^1}$$

$$3420 := \frac{3^7 + 4^6 + 2^{16} + 0^0}{3^0 + 4^1 + 2^4 + 0^1}$$

$$3421 := \frac{-3^7 + 4^7 - 2^9 - 1^0}{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3422 := \frac{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^{13} + 2^{18}}{3^1 + 4^1 + 2^3 + 2^6}$$

$$3422 := \frac{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^{13} + 2^{18}}{3^1 + 4^1 + 2^3 + 2^6}$$

$$3423 := \frac{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^{14} + 3^6}{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$3423 := \frac{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^{14} + 3^6}{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$3424 := \frac{3^8 - 4^0 + 2^5 + 4^4}{-3^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3425 := \frac{3^8 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 5^5}{3^0 + 4^1 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$3425 := \frac{3^8 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 5^5}{3^0 + 4^1 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$3426 := \frac{3^6 + 4^2 + 2^{14} + 6^0}{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$3426 := \frac{3^6 + 4^2 + 2^{14} + 6^0}{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$3427 := \frac{3^4 + 4^6 + 2^{14} + 7^0}{3^1 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3427 := \frac{3^4 + 4^6 + 2^{14} + 7^0}{3^1 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3428 := \frac{3^5 + 4^0 + 2^{14} + 8^3}{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$3428 := \frac{3^5 + 4^0 + 2^{14} + 8^3}{3^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$3429 := \frac{3^6 + 4^3 + 2^{15} + 9^3}{3^0 + 4^1 + 2^2 + 9^0}$$

$$3430 := \frac{3^3 + 4^7 + 3^{10} + 0^1}{3^1 + 4^2 + 3^1 + 0^1}$$

$$3430 := \frac{3^3 + 4^7 + 3^{10} + 0^1}{3^1 + 4^2 + 3^1 + 0^1}$$

$$3431 := \frac{-3^8 - 4^5 + 3^{10} + 1^0}{3^0 + 4^1 + 3^2 + 1^0}$$

$$3432 := \frac{3^5 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 2^1}{3^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 2^2}$$

$$3433 := \frac{3^2 + 4^6 + 3^5 + 3^9}{3^0 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3433 := \frac{3^2 + 4^6 + 3^5 + 3^9}{3^0 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3434 := \frac{3^1 + 4^4 + 3^9 + 4^6}{3^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3434 := \frac{3^1 + 4^4 + 3^9 + 4^6}{3^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3435 := \frac{3^0 + 4^{10} + 3^9 + 5^2}{3^1 + 4^3 + 3^5 + 5^0}$$

$$3436 := \frac{3^8 + 4^4 + 3^{13} + 6^2}{3^1 + 4^1 + 3^5 + 6^3}$$

$$3437 := \frac{3^0 + 4^7 + 3^2 + 7^6}{3^0 + 4^1 + 3^3 + 7^1}$$

$$3438 := \frac{3^9 + 4^3 + 3^9 + 8^5}{3^0 + 4^2 + 3^1 + 8^0}$$

$$3438 := \frac{3^9 + 4^3 + 3^9 + 8^5}{3^0 + 4^2 + 3^1 + 8^0}$$

$$3439 := \frac{3^2 + 4^6 + 3^7 + 9^5}{3^1 + 4^1 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3439 := \frac{3^2 + 4^6 + 3^7 + 9^5}{3^1 + 4^1 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3440 := \frac{3^8 + 4^3 + 4^4 - 0^0}{-3^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$3441 := \frac{3^8 + 4^3 + 4^4 + 1^0}{-3^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3442 := \frac{-3^2 - 4^0 + 4^8 - 2^7}{3^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 2^4}$$

$$3443 := \frac{3^5 + 4^4 + 4^9 + 3^9}{3^0 + 4^2 + 4^3 + 3^0}$$

$$3443 := \frac{3^5 + 4^4 + 4^9 + 3^9}{3^0 + 4^2 + 4^3 + 3^0}$$

$$3444 := \frac{3^5 + 4^0 + 4^{10} + 4^{10}}{3^4 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 4^4}$$

$$3444 := \frac{3^5 + 4^0 + 4^{10} + 4^{10}}{3^4 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 4^4}$$

$$3445 := \frac{3^8 + 4^1 + 4^9 + 5^0}{3^2 + 4^1 + 4^3 + 5^0}$$

$$3445 := \frac{3^8 + 4^1 + 4^9 + 5^0}{3^2 + 4^1 + 4^3 + 5^0}$$

$$3446 := \frac{3^0 - 4^3 + 4^8 + 6^0}{3^0 + 4^0 + 4^2 + 6^0}$$

$$3447 := \frac{3^{11} + 4^5 + 4^5 + 7^2}{3^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 7^2}$$

$$3447 := \frac{3^{11} + 4^5 + 4^5 + 7^2}{3^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 7^2}$$

$$3448 := \frac{-3^2 - 4^2 + 4^8 + 8^0}{3^1 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 8^1}$$

$$3449 := \frac{3^4 + 4^0 + 4^6 - 9^3}{-3^0 - 4^0 + 4^1 - 9^0}$$

$$3450 := \frac{3^2 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 0^1}{3^0 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 0^0}$$

$$3450 := \frac{3^2 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 0^1}{3^0 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 0^0}$$

$$3451 := \frac{3^3 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 1^0}{3^0 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3451 := \frac{3^3 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 1^0}{3^0 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3452 := \frac{3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 2^3}{3^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3452 := \frac{3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 2^3}{3^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3453 := \frac{3^3 + 4^5 + 5^7 + 3^5}{3^0 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 3^0}$$

$$3454 := \frac{3^5 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 4^7}{3^1 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3455 := \frac{3^{10} + 4^8 + 5^3 + 5^5}{3^1 + 4^1 + 5^1 + 5^2}$$

$$3455 := \frac{3^{10} + 4^8 + 5^3 + 5^5}{3^1 + 4^1 + 5^1 + 5^2}$$

$$3456 := \frac{3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 6^5}{3^0 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3456 := \frac{3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 6^5}{3^0 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3457 := \frac{3^{11} + 4^5 + 5^7 + 7^5}{3^0 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^2}$$

$$3458 := \frac{3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 8^4}{3^1 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3458 := \frac{3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 8^4}{3^1 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3459 := \frac{3^7 + 4^{12} + 5^3 + 9^2}{3^0 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 9^3}$$

$$3459 := \frac{3^7 + 4^{12} + 5^3 + 9^2}{3^0 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 9^3}$$

$$3460 := \frac{3^{14} - 4^7 + 6^4 - 0^0}{3^4 + 4^0 + 6^4 + 0^1}$$

$$3461 := \frac{3^{12} + 4^4 + 6^4 + 1^0}{3^0 - 4^3 + 6^3 + 1^0}$$

$$3462 := \frac{3^9 + 4^3 + 6^0 + 2^{10}}{3^1 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3462 := \frac{3^9 + 4^3 + 6^0 + 2^{10}}{3^1 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3463 := \frac{3^7 + 4^1 + 6^6 + 3^8}{3^1 + 4^1 + 6^1 + 3^1}$$

$$3463 := \frac{3^7 + 4^1 + 6^6 + 3^8}{3^1 + 4^1 + 6^1 + 3^1}$$

$$3464 := \frac{3^5 + 4^0 + 6^2 + 4^8}{3^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 4^2}$$

$$3464 := \frac{3^5 + 4^0 + 6^2 + 4^8}{3^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 4^2}$$

$$3465 := \frac{3^9 + 4^4 + 6^5 + 5^1}{3^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 5^1}$$

$$3465 := \frac{3^9 + 4^4 + 6^5 + 5^1}{3^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 5^1}$$

$$3466 := \frac{3^7 - 4^2 - 6^0 + 6^4}{-3^0 + 4^1 - 6^0 - 6^0}$$

$$3467 := \frac{-3^5 - 4^4 + 6^5 - 7^3}{-3^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3468 := \frac{3^7 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^0}{-3^0 + 4^1 - 6^0 - 8^0}$$

$$3469 := \frac{3^7 + 4^7 + 6^6 + 9^6}{3^4 + 4^1 + 6^1 + 9^2}$$

$$3469 := \frac{3^7 + 4^7 + 6^6 + 9^6}{3^4 + 4^1 + 6^1 + 9^2}$$

$$3470 := \frac{3^9 - 4^2 + 7^7 + 0^1}{3^5 - 4^0 + 7^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3471 := \frac{3^{14} - 4^8 - 7^3 - 1^0}{-3^2 + 4^5 + 7^3 + 1^0}$$

$$3472 := \frac{3^2 + 4^6 + 7^3 + 2^{14}}{3^1 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3472 := \frac{3^2 + 4^6 + 7^3 + 2^{14}}{3^1 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3473 := \frac{3^3 + 4^8 + 7^3 + 3^4}{3^0 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3473 := \frac{3^3 + 4^8 + 7^3 + 3^4}{3^0 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3474 := \frac{3^2 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 4^8}{3^1 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 4^2}$$

$$3475 := \frac{3^7 + 4^3 + 7^6 + 5^6}{3^1 + 4^1 + 7^1 + 5^2}$$

$$3476 := \frac{3^5 + 4^8 + 7^2 + 6^3}{3^0 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3477 := \frac{3^1 + 4^5 + 7^2 + 7^4}{-3^0 + 4^1 - 7^0 - 7^0}$$

$$3478 := \frac{3^3 + 4^8 + 7^1 + 8^3}{3^0 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3478 := \frac{3^3 + 4^8 + 7^1 + 8^3}{3^0 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3479 := \frac{3^6 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 9^4}{3^0 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3479 := \frac{3^6 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 9^4}{3^0 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3480 := \frac{-3^8 + 4^7 + 8^4 + 0^0}{3^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 0^0}$$

$$3481 := \frac{3^{17} + 4^2 + 8^5 + 1^0}{3^5 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 1^0}$$

$$3481 := \frac{3^{17} + 4^2 + 8^5 + 1^0}{3^5 + 4^6 + 8^5 + 1^0}$$

$$3482 := \frac{3^0 + 4^5 + 8^0 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3482 := \frac{3^0 + 4^5 + 8^0 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3483 := \frac{3^0 + 4^8 + 8^4 + 3^3}{3^2 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 3^2}$$

$$3483 := \frac{3^0 + 4^8 + 8^4 + 3^3}{3^2 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 3^2}$$

$$3484 := \frac{-3^{10} + 4^0 + 8^6 - 4^5}{3^0 + 4^0 - 8^1 + 4^3}$$

$$3485 := \frac{3^9 + 4^6 + 8^4 + 5^1}{3^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 5^1}$$

$$3485 := \frac{3^9 + 4^6 + 8^4 + 5^1}{3^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 5^1}$$

$$3486 := \frac{3^1 + 4^8 + 8^6 + 6^0}{3^4 + 4^1 + 8^1 + 6^0}$$

$$3486 := \frac{3^1 + 4^8 + 8^6 + 6^0}{3^4 + 4^1 + 8^1 + 6^0}$$

$$3487 := \frac{3^1 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 7^5}{3^1 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3487 := \frac{3^1 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 7^5}{3^1 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3488 := \frac{3^8 + 4^5 - 8^0 - 8^4}{-3^0 + 4^1 - 8^0 - 8^0}$$

$$3489 := \frac{3^{10} + 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^5}{3^0 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3489 := \frac{3^{10} + 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^5}{3^0 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3492 := \frac{3^3 + 4^4 + 9^5 + 2^5}{3^1 + 4^0 + 9^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3493 := \frac{3^4 + 4^{10} + 9^4 + 3^{10}}{3^1 + 4^3 + 9^1 + 3^5}$$

$$3493 := \frac{3^4 + 4^{10} + 9^4 + 3^{10}}{3^1 + 4^3 + 9^1 + 3^5}$$

$$3494 := \frac{3^9 + 4^4 + 9^0 + 4^5}{3^1 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3494 := \frac{3^9 + 4^4 + 9^0 + 4^5}{3^1 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3495 := \frac{3^5 + 4^8 + 9^0 + 5^4}{3^0 + 4^1 + 9^1 + 5^1}$$

$$3495 := \frac{3^5 + 4^8 + 9^0 + 5^4}{3^0 + 4^1 + 9^1 + 5^1}$$

$$3496 := \frac{3^9 + 4^1 + 9^2 + 6^6}{3^0 + 4^2 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3497 := \frac{3^0 + 4^9 + 9^2 + 7^2}{3^0 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 7^2}$$

$$3497 := \frac{3^0 + 4^9 + 9^2 + 7^2}{3^0 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 7^2}$$

$$3498 := \frac{3^9 + 4^3 + 9^3 + 8^3}{3^1 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3498 := \frac{3^9 + 4^3 + 9^3 + 8^3}{3^1 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3499 := \frac{3^0 - 4^1 - 9^4 + 9^5}{3^0 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 9^1}$$

$$3502 := \frac{3^9 - 5^3 + 0^1 - 2^{11}}{3^0 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3504 := \frac{3^1 + 5^7 + 0^1 + 4^8}{-3^0 + 5^2 + 0^0 + 4^2}$$

$$3505 := \frac{3^{12} + 5^4 - 0^0 + 5^{10}}{3^7 + 5^3 + 0^0 + 5^4}$$

$$3506 := \frac{-3^4 + 5^4 + 0^1 + 6^7}{-3^2 + 5^3 + 0^1 - 6^2}$$

$$3507 := \frac{3^6 - 5^0 + 0^1 + 7^5}{3^1 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 7^0}$$

$$3508 := \frac{3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5}{3^0 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 8^1}$$

$$3508 := \frac{3^7 + 5^3 + 0^1 + 8^5}{3^0 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 8^1}$$

$$3509 := \frac{3^6 - 5^3 + 0^1 + 9^5}{3^1 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3513 := \frac{3^9 + 5^9 + 1^0 + 3^{11}}{3^5 + 5^3 + 1^0 + 3^5}$$

$$3513 := \frac{3^9 + 5^9 + 1^0 + 3^{11}}{3^5 + 5^3 + 1^0 + 3^5}$$

$$3517 := \frac{3^{13} - 5^1 - 1^0 + 7^4}{-3^6 - 5^6 + 1^0 + 7^5}$$

$$3518 := \frac{-3^6 + 5^7 - 1^0 + 8^0}{-3^0 + 5^2 - 1^0 - 8^0}$$

$$3519 := \frac{3^{10} + 5^6 - 1^0 + 9^5}{3^1 + 5^2 + 1^0 + 9^1}$$

$$3520 := \frac{3^{12} - 5^8 - 2^4 + 0^1}{3^1 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 0^1}$$

$$3521 := \frac{3^{13} - 5^9 + 2^{19} + 1^0}{3^2 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 1^0}$$

$$3522 := \frac{3^3 + 5^4 + 2^{12} + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 2^1}$$

$$3522 := \frac{3^3 + 5^4 + 2^{12} + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 2^1}$$

$$3523 := \frac{3^9 + 5^1 + 2^{14} + 3^{10}}{3^0 + 5^0 + 2^4 + 3^2}$$

$$3524 := \frac{3^5 + 5^3 + 2^{15} + 4^8}{3^0 + 5^2 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3524 := \frac{3^5 + 5^3 + 2^{15} + 4^8}{3^0 + 5^2 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3525 := \frac{3^{11} + 5^1 + 2^{11} + 5^7}{3^1 + 5^0 + 2^6 + 5^1}$$

$$3526 := \frac{3^7 + 5^6 + 2^{11} + 6^4}{3^1 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3526 := \frac{3^7 + 5^6 + 2^{11} + 6^4}{3^1 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3527 := \frac{3^{13} + 5^{10} + 2^9 + 7^1}{3^4 + 5^5 + 2^3 + 7^1}$$

$$3528 := \frac{3^5 + 5^3 + 2^{19} + 8^5}{3^2 + 5^3 + 2^4 + 8^1}$$

$$3528 := \frac{3^5 + 5^3 + 2^{19} + 8^5}{3^2 + 5^3 + 2^4 + 8^1}$$

$$3529 := \frac{3^2 + 5^7 + 2^0 + 9^4}{3^2 + 5^1 + 2^0 + 9^1}$$

$$3529 := \frac{3^2 + 5^7 + 2^0 + 9^4}{3^2 + 5^1 + 2^0 + 9^1}$$

$$3530 := \frac{-3^2 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 0^0}{3^0 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 0^0}$$

$$3531 := \frac{3^0 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 1^0}{3^0 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3531 := \frac{3^0 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 1^0}{3^0 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3532 := \frac{3^8 + 5^6 + 3^{10} + 2^0}{3^0 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 2^4}$$

$$3532 := \frac{3^8 + 5^6 + 3^{10} + 2^0}{3^0 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 2^4}$$

$$3533 := \frac{3^1 + 5^1 + 3^8 + 3^{11}}{3^2 + 5^2 + 3^2 + 3^2}$$

$$3533 := \frac{3^1 + 5^1 + 3^8 + 3^{11}}{3^2 + 5^2 + 3^2 + 3^2}$$

$$3534 := \frac{3^7 + 5^1 + 3^{12} + 4^0}{3^0 + 5^1 + 3^4 + 4^3}$$

$$3534 := \frac{3^7 + 5^1 + 3^{12} + 4^0}{3^0 + 5^1 + 3^4 + 4^3}$$

$$3535 := \frac{3^2 - 5^3 + 3^8 + 5^4}{-3^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3536 := \frac{3^6 + 5^7 + 3^{10} + 6^0}{3^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 6^2}$$

$$3536 := \frac{3^6 + 5^7 + 3^{10} + 6^0}{3^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 6^2}$$

$$3537 := \frac{3^3 + 5^3 + 3^{10} + 7^6}{3^2 + 5^2 + 3^2 + 7^1}$$

$$3537 := \frac{3^3 + 5^3 + 3^{10} + 7^6}{3^2 + 5^2 + 3^2 + 7^1}$$

$$3538 := \frac{-3^5 - 5^1 + 3^{11} + 8^0}{-3^0 + 5^2 + 3^3 - 8^0}$$

$$3539 := \frac{3^0 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^2}{3^0 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3539 := \frac{3^0 + 5^6 + 3^9 + 9^2}{3^0 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3540 := \frac{-3^5 + 5^7 - 4^0 - 0^0}{3^0 + 5^1 + 4^2 + 0^1}$$

$$3541 := \frac{3^{10} + 5^3 + 4^5 - 1^0}{-3^0 + 5^0 + 4^2 + 1^0}$$

$$3542 := \frac{3^9 + 5^3 + 4^6 + 2^{15}}{3^1 + 5^0 + 4^1 + 2^3}$$

$$3542 := \frac{3^9 + 5^3 + 4^6 + 2^{15}}{3^1 + 5^0 + 4^1 + 2^3}$$

$$3543 := \frac{3^0 + 5^2 + 4^0 + 3^{13}}{3^4 + 5^3 + 4^0 + 3^5}$$

$$3544 := \frac{3^9 + 5^1 + 4^5 + 4^6}{3^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3544 := \frac{3^9 + 5^1 + 4^5 + 4^6}{3^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3545 := \frac{-3^6 + 5^3 + 4^5 + 5^5}{-3^0 - 5^0 + 4^1 - 5^0}$$

$$3546 := \frac{3^7 + 5^3 + 4^6 + 6^5}{3^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3546 := \frac{3^7 + 5^3 + 4^6 + 6^5}{3^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3547 := \frac{3^{12} + 5^5 + 4^5 + 7^1}{3^1 + 5^3 + 4^2 + 7^1}$$

$$3547 := \frac{3^{12} + 5^5 + 4^5 + 7^1}{3^1 + 5^3 + 4^2 + 7^1}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 3548 := \frac{3^9 + 5^7 + 4^5 + 8^3}{3^0 + 5^2 + 4^0 + 8^0} & 3560 := \frac{-3^6 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 0^1}{-3^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 0^0} & 3573 := \frac{3^7 + 5^7 + 7^2 + 3^9}{3^0 + 5^2 + 7^0 + 3^0} \\
 3548 := \frac{3^9 + 5^7 + 4^5 + 8^3}{3^0 + 5^2 + 4^0 + 8^0} & 3561 := \frac{3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 1^0}{-3^0 - 5^0 + 6^1 + 1^0} & 3573 := \frac{3^7 + 5^7 + 7^2 + 3^9}{3^0 + 5^2 + 7^0 + 3^0} \\
 3549 := \frac{3^{10} + 5^1 + 4^7 + 9^6}{3^0 + 5^2 + 4^3 + 9^2} & 3562 := \frac{3^7 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 2^{10}}{3^0 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 2^1} & 3574 := \frac{3^1 + 5^8 + 7^5 + 4^0}{3^4 + 5^2 + 7^1 + 4^0} \\
 3549 := \frac{3^{10} + 5^1 + 4^7 + 9^6}{3^0 + 5^2 + 4^3 + 9^2} & 3562 := \frac{3^7 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 2^{10}}{3^0 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 2^1} & 3574 := \frac{3^1 + 5^8 + 7^5 + 4^0}{3^4 + 5^2 + 7^1 + 4^0} \\
 3550 := \frac{3^{10} - 5^3 + 5^6 + 0^0}{3^0 - 5^1 + 5^2 + 0^1} & 3563 := \frac{3^8 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 3^{12}}{3^2 + 5^2 + 6^2 + 3^4} & 3575 := \frac{3^{10} - 5^5 - 7^2 + 5^6}{3^1 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 5^1} \\
 3551 := \frac{-3^0 - 5^0 + 5^7 - 1^0}{-3^0 - 5^0 + 5^2 - 1^0} & 3563 := \frac{3^8 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 3^{12}}{3^2 + 5^2 + 6^2 + 3^4} & 3577 := \frac{3^1 + 5^8 + 7^3 + 7^5}{3^4 + 5^2 + 7^0 + 7^1} \\
 3552 := \frac{3^{11} + 5^2 - 5^5 + 2^0}{3^1 + 5^1 + 5^2 + 2^4} & 3564 := \frac{3^{10} + 5^5 + 6^1 + 4^9}{3^0 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 4^3} & 3577 := \frac{3^1 + 5^8 + 7^3 + 7^5}{3^4 + 5^2 + 7^0 + 7^1} \\
 3553 := \frac{3^2 + 5^1 + 5^7 + 3^3}{3^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 3^2} & 3564 := \frac{3^{10} + 5^5 + 6^1 + 4^9}{3^0 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 4^3} & 3578 := \frac{3^{10} - 5^4 + 7^4 + 8^0}{3^0 + 5^0 + 7^1 + 8^1} \\
 3553 := \frac{3^2 + 5^1 + 5^7 + 3^3}{3^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 3^2} & 3565 := \frac{-3^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 5^5}{-3^0 - 5^0 + 6^1 - 5^0} & 3579 := \frac{3^9 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 9^5}{3^0 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 9^1} \\
 3554 := \frac{3^{11} + 5^3 - 5^5 - 4^0}{3^1 + 5^1 + 5^2 + 4^2} & 3566 := \frac{3^{11} + 5^5 + 6^4 + 6^6}{3^3 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 6^1} & 3579 := \frac{3^9 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 9^5}{3^0 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 9^1} \\
 3555 := \frac{3^4 - 5^0 + 5^1 + 5^7}{-3^0 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 5^2} & 3567 := \frac{3^4 + 5^7 + 6^4 + 7^5}{3^2 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 7^1} & 3580 := \frac{3^{11} + 5^6 + 8^5 + 0^1}{-3^0 - 5^0 + 8^2 + 0^0} \\
 3556 := \frac{3^{10} + 5^0 + 5^6 + 6^0}{3^2 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 6^1} & 3567 := \frac{3^4 + 5^7 + 6^4 + 7^5}{3^2 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 7^1} & 3581 := \frac{-3^6 - 5^0 + 8^6 - 1^0}{3^1 + 5^1 + 8^2 + 1^0} \\
 3556 := \frac{3^{10} + 5^0 + 5^6 + 6^0}{3^2 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 6^1} & 3568 := \frac{-3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^3}{-3^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 8^0} & 3582 := \frac{3^8 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^{15}}{3^1 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 2^4} \\
 3557 := \frac{3^1 + 5^3 + 5^7 + 7^0}{3^2 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 7^1} & 3569 := \frac{3^7 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 9^2}{-3^0 - 5^0 - 6^1 + 9^1} & 3582 := \frac{3^8 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^{15}}{3^1 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 2^4} \\
 3557 := \frac{3^1 + 5^3 + 5^7 + 7^0}{3^2 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 7^1} & 3570 := \frac{3^{11} + 5^6 + 7^1 + 0^0}{3^1 + 5^0 + 7^2 + 0^0} & 3583 := \frac{3^2 + 5^6 + 8^4 + 3^9}{3^0 + 5^0 + 8^1 + 3^0} \\
 3558 := \frac{3^3 + 5^3 + 5^7 - 8^0}{-3^0 - 5^0 + 5^2 - 8^0} & 3570 := \frac{3^{11} + 5^6 + 7^1 + 0^0}{3^1 + 5^0 + 7^2 + 0^0} & 3583 := \frac{3^2 + 5^6 + 8^4 + 3^9}{3^0 + 5^0 + 8^1 + 3^0} \\
 3559 := \frac{3^6 + 5^0 + 5^7 + 9^4}{3^2 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 9^1} & 3571 := \frac{3^7 + 5^8 - 7^0 - 1^0}{-3^2 + 5^3 - 7^1 + 1^0} & 3584 := \frac{3^3 + 5^9 + 8^2 + 4^3}{3^3 + 5^1 + 8^3 + 4^0} \\
 3559 := \frac{3^6 + 5^0 + 5^7 + 9^4}{3^2 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 9^1} & 3572 := \frac{3^7 + 5^6 + 7^2 - 2^0}{3^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 2^1} & 3584 := \frac{3^3 + 5^9 + 8^2 + 4^3}{3^3 + 5^1 + 8^3 + 4^0}
 \end{array}$$

$$3585 := \frac{3^{11} + 5^7 + 8^1 + 5^7}{3^1 + 5^0 + 8^2 + 5^2}$$

$$3585 := \frac{3^{11} + 5^7 + 8^1 + 5^7}{3^1 + 5^0 + 8^2 + 5^2}$$

$$3586 := \frac{3^9 + 5^2 + 8^3 + 6^4}{3^1 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3586 := \frac{3^9 + 5^2 + 8^3 + 6^4}{3^1 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3587 := \frac{-3^0 + 5^5 + 8^3 - 7^2}{3^0 + 5^0 - 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3588 := \frac{3^9 + 5^6 + 8^2 + 8^4}{3^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$3588 := \frac{3^9 + 5^6 + 8^2 + 8^4}{3^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$3589 := \frac{3^5 + 5^8 + 8^2 + 9^6}{3^5 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3589 := \frac{3^5 + 5^8 + 8^2 + 9^6}{3^5 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3590 := \frac{-3^9 + 5^3 + 9^5 - 0^0}{3^0 + 5^0 + 9^1 + 0^1}$$

$$3591 := \frac{-3^1 + 5^4 + 9^4 - 1^0}{-3^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3592 := \frac{-3^0 + 5^4 + 9^4 - 2^0}{-3^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3593 := \frac{3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9}{3^0 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 3^1}$$

$$3593 := \frac{3^8 + 5^5 + 9^4 + 3^9}{3^0 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 3^1}$$

$$3593 := \frac{3^4 + 5^4 + 9^4 - 3^4}{3^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 - 3^0}$$

$$3594 := \frac{3^0 + 5^4 + 9^4 + 4^0}{-3^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3595 := \frac{3^4 + 5^5 + 9^7 + 5^8}{3^4 + 5^1 + 9^3 + 5^4}$$

$$3595 := \frac{3^4 + 5^5 + 9^7 + 5^8}{3^4 + 5^1 + 9^3 + 5^4}$$

$$3597 := \frac{3^3 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 7^6}{3^2 + 5^2 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3597 := \frac{3^3 + 5^5 + 9^5 + 7^6}{3^2 + 5^2 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3598 := \frac{3^2 + 5^4 + 9^4 + 8^0}{-3^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3599 := \frac{3^5 + 5^7 + 9^2 + 9^3}{3^1 + 5^0 + 9^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3599 := \frac{3^5 + 5^7 + 9^2 + 9^3}{3^1 + 5^0 + 9^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3602 := \frac{-3^1 + 6^7 - 0^0 + 2^{10}}{3^2 + 6^2 + 0^0 + 2^5}$$

$$3603 := \frac{3^3 + 6^8 + 0^1 + 3^8}{3^2 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 3^5}$$

$$3603 := \frac{3^3 + 6^8 + 0^1 + 3^8}{3^2 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 3^5}$$

$$3604 := \frac{3^{11} - 6^5 + 0^0 + 4^2}{3^2 + 6^2 + 0^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3607 := \frac{3^5 + 6^6 - 0^0 - 7^1}{-3^0 + 6^1 + 0^0 + 7^1}$$

$$3608 := \frac{-3^4 - 6^3 + 0^0 + 8^5}{3^0 + 6^1 + 0^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3609 := \frac{-3^2 - 6^4 + 0^1 + 9^5}{3^0 + 6^1 + 0^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3612 := \frac{3^7 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 2^7}{-3^0 - 6^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3614 := \frac{3^3 + 6^7 + 1^0 + 4^7}{3^4 - 6^0 + 1^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3615 := \frac{3^{11} - 6^1 - 1^0 - 5^1}{3^2 + 6^2 - 1^0 + 5^1}$$

$$3617 := \frac{-3^4 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 7^4}{-3^0 - 6^1 + 1^0 + 7^1}$$

$$3617 := \frac{-3^4 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 7^4}{-3^0 - 6^1 + 1^0 + 7^1}$$

$$3617 := \frac{-3^4 + 6^4 + 1^4 + 7^4}{3^1 + 6^1 - 1^1 - 7^1}$$

$$3618 := \frac{-3^3 + 6^5 - 1^0 - 8^3}{-3^0 + 6^0 + 1^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3620 := \frac{3^3 + 6^6 + 2^{16} + 0^0}{3^2 + 6^1 + 2^4 + 0^1}$$

$$3620 := \frac{3^3 + 6^6 + 2^{16} + 0^0}{3^2 + 6^1 + 2^4 + 0^1}$$

$$3621 := \frac{3^9 - 6^1 + 2^{11} + 1^0}{3^1 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3622 := \frac{3^9 + 6^0 + 2^{10} + 2^{10}}{3^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 2^1}$$

$$3622 := \frac{3^9 + 6^0 + 2^{10} + 2^{10}}{3^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 2^1}$$

$$3623 := \frac{3^3 + 6^5 + 2^7 + 3^8}{3^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3623 := \frac{3^3 + 6^5 + 2^7 + 3^8}{3^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3624 := \frac{-3^6 + 6^0 + 2^8 + 4^6}{-3^0 - 6^0 - 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3625 := \frac{3^3 + 6^6 + 2^{13} + 5^5}{3^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 5^1}$$

$$3626 := \frac{3^{10} + 6^4 + 2^0 + 6^4}{3^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3626 := \frac{3^{10} + 6^4 + 2^0 + 6^4}{3^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3627 := \frac{3^3 + 6^6 + 2^{15} + 7^3}{3^0 + 6^1 + 2^3 + 7^1}$$

$$3627 := \frac{3^3 + 6^6 + 2^{15} + 7^3}{3^0 + 6^1 + 2^3 + 7^1}$$

$$3628 := \frac{3^9 + 6^2 + 2^{11} + 8^0}{3^1 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3628 := \frac{3^9 + 6^2 + 2^{11} + 8^0}{3^1 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3629 := \frac{3^0 + 6^2 + 2^4 + 9^7}{3^2 + 6^4 + 2^2 + 9^1}$$

$$3629 := \frac{3^0 + 6^2 + 2^4 + 9^7}{3^2 + 6^4 + 2^2 + 9^1}$$

$$3630 := \frac{3^6 - 6^1 + 3^{11} + 0^1}{3^1 + 6^2 + 3^2 + 0^0}$$

$$3632 := \frac{3^3 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 2^{18}}{3^0 + 6^1 + 3^1 + 2^6}$$

$$3632 := \frac{3^3 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 2^{18}}{3^0 + 6^1 + 3^1 + 2^6}$$

$$3633 := \frac{3^3 + 6^5 + 3^3 + 3^{13}}{3^4 + 6^2 + 3^4 + 3^5}$$

$$3633 := \frac{3^3 + 6^5 + 3^3 + 3^{13}}{3^4 + 6^2 + 3^4 + 3^5}$$

$$3634 := \frac{3^3 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 4^8}{3^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 4^2}$$

$$3634 := \frac{3^3 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 4^8}{3^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 4^2}$$

$$3635 := \frac{3^3 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 5^3}{3^0 - 6^1 + 3^0 + 5^1}$$

$$3636 := \frac{3^2 + 6^3 - 3^6 + 6^5}{-3^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3637 := \frac{3^5 + 6^{10} + 3^7 + 7^8}{3^3 + 6^4 + 3^4 + 7^5}$$

$$3637 := \frac{3^5 + 6^{10} + 3^7 + 7^8}{3^3 + 6^4 + 3^4 + 7^5}$$

$$3638 := \frac{3^8 + 6^7 + 3^{10} + 8^2}{3^1 + 6^0 + 3^3 + 8^2}$$

$$3638 := \frac{3^8 + 6^7 + 3^{10} + 8^2}{3^1 + 6^0 + 3^3 + 8^2}$$

$$3639 := \frac{3^2 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 9^6}{3^1 + 6^2 + 3^3 + 9^2}$$

$$3639 := \frac{3^2 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 9^6}{3^1 + 6^2 + 3^3 + 9^2}$$

$$3640 := \frac{3^6 + 6^6 - 4^3 - 0^0}{3^1 + 6^1 + 4^1 + 0^1}$$

$$3641 := \frac{3^0 + 6^1 + 4^9 + 1^0}{3^0 + 6^1 + 4^3 + 1^0}$$

$$3641 := \frac{3^0 + 6^1 + 4^9 + 1^0}{3^0 + 6^1 + 4^3 + 1^0}$$

$$3642 := \frac{3^1 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 2^{15}}{3^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3642 := \frac{3^1 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 2^{15}}{3^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3643 := \frac{3^{10} + 6^9 + 4^{10} + 3^{13}}{3^2 + 6^4 + 4^2 + 3^7}$$

$$3643 := \frac{3^{10} + 6^9 + 4^{10} + 3^{13}}{3^2 + 6^4 + 4^2 + 3^7}$$

$$3644 := \frac{3^3 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 4^7}{3^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3644 := \frac{3^3 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 4^7}{3^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3645 := \frac{-3^3 + 6^1 - 4^5 + 5^6}{3^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3646 := \frac{3^{11} - 6^0 + 4^5 + 6^5}{-3^0 - 6^1 + 4^3 - 6^1}$$

$$3647 := \frac{-3^7 - 6^2 + 4^1 + 7^5}{3^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3648 := \frac{3^3 + 6^2 + 4^0 + 8^5}{3^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3648 := \frac{3^3 + 6^2 + 4^0 + 8^5}{3^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3649 := \frac{3^1 + 6^5 + 4^4 + 9^4}{3^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3649 := \frac{3^1 + 6^5 + 4^4 + 9^4}{3^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3650 := \frac{-3^4 + 6^1 + 5^8 + 0^1}{3^4 + 6^0 + 5^2 + 0^1}$$

$$3651 := \frac{3^8 + 6^3 - 5^5 - 1^0}{3^0 - 6^1 + 5^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3652 := \frac{3^7 + 6^3 + 5^5 + 2^{14}}{3^1 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3653 := \frac{3^3 + 6^3 + 5^{12} + 3^4}{3^1 + 6^5 + 5^1 + 3^{10}}$$

$$3653 := \frac{3^3 + 6^3 + 5^{12} + 3^4}{3^1 + 6^5 + 5^1 + 3^{10}}$$

$$3654 := \frac{3^9 + 6^5 + 5^1 + 4^7}{3^0 + 6^1 + 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3654 := \frac{3^9 + 6^5 + 5^1 + 4^7}{3^0 + 6^1 + 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3655 := \frac{3^6 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 5^3}{3^0 + 6^1 + 5^0 + 5^1}$$

$$3655 := \frac{3^6 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 5^3}{3^0 + 6^1 + 5^0 + 5^1}$$

$$3656 := \frac{3^3 + 6^7 + 5^5 + 6^7}{3^3 + 6^0 + 5^3 + 6^0}$$

$$3656 := \frac{3^3 + 6^7 + 5^5 + 6^7}{3^3 + 6^0 + 5^3 + 6^0}$$

$$3657 := \frac{3^{11} + 6^4 + 5^3 + 7^6}{3^0 + 6^1 + 5^2 + 7^2}$$

$$3658 := \frac{3^9 + 6^7 + 5^8 + 8^7}{3^2 + 6^3 + 5^2 + 8^3}$$

$$3658 := \frac{3^9 + 6^7 + 5^8 + 8^7}{3^2 + 6^3 + 5^2 + 8^3}$$

$$3659 := \frac{3^9 - 6^1 - 5^4 + 9^4}{-3^0 + 6^1 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3662 := \frac{3^4 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 2^{13}}{3^0 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 2^1}$$

$$3662 := \frac{3^4 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 2^{13}}{3^0 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 2^1}$$

$$3663 := \frac{3^{10} + 6^3 + 6^6 + 3^{12}}{3^4 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 3^4}$$

$$3663 := \frac{3^{10} + 6^3 + 6^6 + 3^{12}}{3^4 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 3^4}$$

$$3664 := \frac{3^7 + 6^0 + 6^7 + 4^1}{3^0 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 4^3}$$

$$3664 := \frac{3^7 + 6^0 + 6^7 + 4^1}{3^0 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 4^3}$$

$$3665 := \frac{3^1 + 6^8 + 6^9 + 5^1}{3^4 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 5^5}$$

$$3665 := \frac{3^1 + 6^8 + 6^9 + 5^1}{3^4 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 5^5}$$

$$3667 := \frac{-3^6 + 6^3 + 6^6 - 7^5}{-3^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 7^1}$$

$$3668 := \frac{3^3 + 6^0 + 6^3 + 8^5}{3^0 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 8^0}$$

$$3668 := \frac{3^3 + 6^0 + 6^3 + 8^5}{3^0 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 8^0}$$

$$3669 := \frac{3^{12} + 6^2 + 6^7 + 9^6}{3^5 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 9^2}$$

$$3669 := \frac{3^{12} + 6^2 + 6^7 + 9^6}{3^5 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 9^2}$$

$$3670 := \frac{3^8 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 0^1}{3^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 0^0}$$

$$3670 := \frac{3^8 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 0^1}{3^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 0^0}$$

$$3671 := \frac{-3^3 + 6^4 + 7^4 + 1^0}{-3^0 - 6^1 + 7^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3672 := \frac{3^8 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 2^3}{3^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3672 := \frac{3^8 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 2^3}{3^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3673 := \frac{3^5 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 3^{11}}{3^1 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 3^1}$$

$$3673 := \frac{3^5 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 3^{11}}{3^1 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 3^1}$$

$$3674 := \frac{3^8 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 4^2}{3^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3675 := \frac{3^{12} + 6^8 + 7^3 + 5^7}{3^5 + 6^2 + 7^3 + 5^0}$$

$$3675 := \frac{3^{12} + 6^8 + 7^3 + 5^7}{3^5 + 6^2 + 7^3 + 5^0}$$

$$3676 := \frac{-3^3 + 6^1 + 7^4 + 6^4}{3^0 + 6^0 - 7^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3677 := \frac{-3^3 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 7^4}{-3^0 - 6^1 + 7^0 + 7^1}$$

$$3678 := \frac{3^{14} + 6^1 + 7^5 + 8^1}{3^0 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 8^0}$$

$$3679 := \frac{3^{12} + 6^1 + 7^3 + 9^6}{3^5 + 6^2 + 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$3679 := \frac{3^{12} + 6^1 + 7^3 + 9^6}{3^5 + 6^2 + 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$3680 := \frac{-3^0 + 6^5 - 8^4 + 0^0}{-3^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3681 := \frac{3^{10} - 6^3 + 8^2 - 1^0}{3^0 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3682 := \frac{3^6 + 6^4 + 8^0 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3682 := \frac{3^6 + 6^4 + 8^0 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3683 := \frac{3^4 + 6^6 + 8^4 + 3^6}{3^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^2}$$

$$3683 := \frac{3^4 + 6^6 + 8^4 + 3^6}{3^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^2}$$

$$3684 := \frac{3^1 + 6^5 + 8^0 - 4^6}{-3^0 - 6^0 - 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3685 := \frac{3^5 + 6^9 + 8^4 + 5^3}{3^7 + 6^2 + 8^3 + 5^0}$$

$$3685 := \frac{3^5 + 6^9 + 8^4 + 5^3}{3^7 + 6^2 + 8^3 + 5^0}$$

$$3685 := \frac{3^5 - 6^5 + 8^5 - 5^5}{-3^1 + 6^1 + 8^1 - 5^1}$$

$$3686 := \frac{3^0 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 6^5}{3^0 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 6^0}$$

$$3686 := \frac{3^0 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 6^5}{3^0 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 6^0}$$

$$3687 := \frac{-3^2 + 6^4 - 8^0 + 7^4}{3^0 + 6^0 - 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3688 := \frac{3^2 + 6^5 - 8^0 - 8^4}{-3^1 + 6^1 - 8^0 - 8^0}$$

$$3689 := \frac{3^1 - 6^2 + 8^1 + 9^5}{3^0 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3690 := \frac{3^9 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 0^1}{3^1 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 0^1}$$

$$3690 := \frac{3^9 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 0^1}{3^1 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 0^1}$$

$$3691 := \frac{3^2 - 6^0 + 9^5 - 1^0}{3^2 - 6^0 + 9^1 - 1^0}$$

$$3692 := \frac{3^2 + 6^1 + 9^4 + 2^{13}}{3^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3693 := \frac{3^9 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 3^9}{3^1 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 3^2}$$

$$3693 := \frac{3^9 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 3^9}{3^1 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 3^2}$$

$$3694 := \frac{3^{11} + 6^3 + 9^5 + 4^1}{3^1 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 4^2}$$

$$3694 := \frac{3^{11} + 6^3 + 9^5 + 4^1}{3^1 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 4^2}$$

$$3695 := \frac{3^1 + 6^4 - 9^3 + 5^5}{3^0 - 6^1 + 9^0 + 5^1}$$

$$3696 := \frac{3^{11} + 6^2 + 9^1 + 6^3}{3^3 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3696 := \frac{3^{11} + 6^2 + 9^1 + 6^3}{3^3 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3697 := \frac{3^7 + 6^2 + 9^6 + 7^4}{3^2 + 6^1 + 9^2 + 7^2}$$

$$3697 := \frac{3^7 + 6^2 + 9^6 + 7^4}{3^2 + 6^1 + 9^2 + 7^2}$$

$$3698 := \frac{3^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 - 8^4}{3^0 + 6^0 - 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$3699 := \frac{3^8 + 6^7 + 9^4 + 9^4}{3^3 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3699 := \frac{3^8 + 6^7 + 9^4 + 9^4}{3^3 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3702 := \frac{3^9 + 7^4 + 0^1 + 2^7}{3^0 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3702 := \frac{3^9 + 7^4 + 0^1 + 2^7}{3^0 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3703 := \frac{3^0 + 7^6 + 0^0 - 3^8}{3^0 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 3^3}$$

$$3704 := \frac{-3^8 - 7^1 + 0^1 + 4^9}{3^1 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 4^3}$$

$$3705 := \frac{-3^9 + 7^7 + 0^1 + 5^3}{-3^0 + 7^3 + 0^1 - 5^3}$$

$$3706 := \frac{3^2 + 7^4 + 0^1 + 6^4}{-3^0 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 6^0}$$

$$3708 := \frac{3^{14} + 7^3 + 0^1 + 8^1}{3^6 + 7^2 + 0^1 + 8^3}$$

$$3708 := \frac{3^{14} + 7^3 + 0^1 + 8^1}{3^6 + 7^2 + 0^1 + 8^3}$$

$$3712 := \frac{3^{10} + 7^3 - 1^0 + 2^0}{3^2 + 7^1 - 1^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3713 := \frac{3^4 - 7^5 - 1^0 + 3^{15}}{3^6 + 7^4 + 1^0 + 3^6}$$

$$3715 := \frac{3^{13} + 7^0 + 1^0 + 5^5}{3^4 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 5^1}$$

$$3715 := \frac{3^{13} + 7^0 + 1^0 + 5^5}{3^4 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 5^1}$$

$$3718 := \frac{3^{11} - 7^4 - 1^0 + 8^0}{-3^2 - 7^1 - 1^0 + 8^2}$$

$$3720 := \frac{3^{10} + 7^3 + 2^7 + 0^1}{3^0 + 7^1 + 2^3 + 0^1}$$

$$3720 := \frac{3^{10} + 7^3 + 2^7 + 0^1}{3^0 + 7^1 + 2^3 + 0^1}$$

$$3721 := \frac{-3^6 + 7^4 + 2^{11} + 1^0}{-3^0 - 7^0 + 2^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3722 := \frac{3^8 + 7^1 + 2^7 + 2^{13}}{3^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3722 := \frac{3^8 + 7^1 + 2^7 + 2^{13}}{3^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3723 := \frac{3^1 + 7^1 + 2^{15} + 3^6}{3^0 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 3^1}$$

$$3724 := \frac{3^9 + 7^4 + 2^2 + 4^4}{3^1 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3725 := \frac{3^7 + 7^2 + 2^{14} + 5^1}{3^0 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$3726 := \frac{3^6 + 7^0 + 2^{15} + 6^2}{3^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 6^1}$$

$$3727 := \frac{3^2 + 7^3 + 2^{14} + 7^5}{3^1 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$3727 := \frac{3^2 + 7^3 + 2^{14} + 7^5}{3^1 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$3728 := \frac{3^6 + 7^5 + 2^{17} + 8^3}{3^2 + 7^1 + 2^4 + 8^1}$$

$$3728 := \frac{3^6 + 7^5 + 2^{17} + 8^3}{3^2 + 7^1 + 2^4 + 8^1}$$

$$3729 := \frac{3^2 + 7^2 + 2^{17} + 9^5}{3^1 + 7^1 + 2^5 + 9^1}$$

$$3729 := \frac{3^2 + 7^2 + 2^{17} + 9^5}{3^1 + 7^1 + 2^5 + 9^1}$$

$$3731 := \frac{3^5 - 7^5 + 3^{12} + 1^0}{3^2 + 7^2 + 3^4 - 1^0}$$

$$3732 := \frac{-3^8 - 7^4 + 3^{12} + 2^0}{3^2 + 7^2 + 3^4 + 2^0}$$

$$3733 := \frac{3^4 + 7^5 + 3^4 + 3^{11}}{3^0 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3733 := \frac{3^4 + 7^5 + 3^4 + 3^{11}}{3^0 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3734 := \frac{-3^{16} - 7^{10} + 3^{18} - 4^0}{-3^0 - 7^2 + 3^5 + 4^7}$$

$$3735 := \frac{3^5 + 7^3 + 3^{10} + 5^3}{3^0 + 7^0 + 3^2 + 5^1}$$

$$3735 := \frac{3^5 + 7^3 + 3^{10} + 5^3}{3^0 + 7^0 + 3^2 + 5^1}$$

$$3736 := \frac{3^6 - 7^0 + 3^{10} - 6^0}{-3^0 + 7^1 + 3^2 + 6^0}$$

$$3737 := \frac{3^6 + 7^1 + 3^{10} + 7^1}{3^0 + 7^1 + 3^0 + 7^1}$$

$$3737 := \frac{3^6 + 7^1 + 3^{10} + 7^1}{3^0 + 7^1 + 3^0 + 7^1}$$

$$3738 := \frac{-3^4 - 7^5 + 3^{13} + 8^0}{-3^0 + 7^3 + 3^4 - 8^0}$$

$$3739 := \frac{3^6 + 7^6 + 3^7 + 9^4}{3^2 + 7^1 + 3^2 + 9^1}$$

$$3739 := \frac{3^6 + 7^6 + 3^7 + 9^4}{3^2 + 7^1 + 3^2 + 9^1}$$

$$3740 := \frac{3^9 + 7^4 + 4^6 + 0^1}{3^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 0^0}$$

$$3740 := \frac{3^9 + 7^4 + 4^6 + 0^1}{3^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 0^0}$$

$$3741 := \frac{-3^4 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 1^0}{-3^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3742 := \frac{3^7 + 7^4 + 4^3 + 2^{15}}{3^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3742 := \frac{3^7 + 7^4 + 4^3 + 2^{15}}{3^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3743 := \frac{-3^0 - 7^3 + 4^6 - 3^2}{-3^0 - 7^0 + 4^1 - 3^0}$$

$$3744 := \frac{3^{10} + 7^3 + 4^4 + 4^4}{3^0 + 7^1 + 4^1 + 4^1}$$

$$3744 := \frac{3^{10} + 7^3 + 4^4 + 4^4}{3^0 + 7^1 + 4^1 + 4^1}$$

$$3745 := \frac{3^7 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 5^5}{3^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$3745 := \frac{3^7 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 5^5}{3^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$3746 := \frac{3^7 + 7^1 + 4^4 + 6^4}{-3^0 - 7^0 + 4^1 - 6^0}$$

$$3747 := \frac{3^9 + 7^2 + 4^6 + 7^4}{3^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 7^0}$$

$$3747 := \frac{3^9 + 7^2 + 4^6 + 7^4}{3^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 7^0}$$

$$3748 := \frac{3^{10} + 7^3 + 4^3 + 8^3}{3^1 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 8^1}$$

$$3748 := \frac{3^{10} + 7^3 + 4^3 + 8^3}{3^1 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 8^1}$$

$$3749 := \frac{3^5 + 7^4 + 4^5 + 9^2}{-3^0 - 7^0 + 4^1 - 9^0}$$

$$3751 := \frac{3^{10} + 7^3 + 5^4 - 1^0}{3^1 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 1^1}$$

$$3752 := \frac{3^{12} + 7^6 + 5^1 + 2^0}{3^2 + 7^1 + 5^3 + 2^5}$$

$$3752 := \frac{3^{12} + 7^6 + 5^1 + 2^0}{3^2 + 7^1 + 5^3 + 2^5}$$

$$3753 := \frac{3^7 + 7^1 + 5^5 + 3^7}{-3^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3754 := \frac{3^{12} + 7^7 + 5^8 + 4^0}{3^4 + 7^3 + 5^2 + 4^2}$$

$$3754 := \frac{3^{12} + 7^7 + 5^8 + 4^0}{3^4 + 7^3 + 5^2 + 4^2}$$

$$3755 := \frac{3^8 + 7^3 + 5^0 + 5^6}{3^1 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3755 := \frac{3^8 + 7^3 + 5^0 + 5^6}{3^1 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3756 := \frac{3^6 + 7^4 + 5^4 + 6^0}{-3^0 + 7^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3757 := \frac{-3^1 - 7^4 + 5^4 + 7^5}{3^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$3758 := \frac{3^{12} + 7^4 + 5^8 + 8^0}{3^5 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3758 := \frac{3^{12} + 7^4 + 5^8 + 8^0}{3^5 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3759 := \frac{-3^9 - 7^5 - 5^1 + 9^5}{3^1 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3760 := \frac{-3^{10} - 7^1 + 6^8 + 0^1}{3^4 + 7^3 + 6^1 + 0^0}$$

$$3761 := \frac{3^7 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 1^0}{-3^0 + 7^1 + 6^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3762 := \frac{3^9 + 7^0 + 6^3 + 2^{15}}{3^1 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3762 := \frac{3^9 + 7^0 + 6^3 + 2^{15}}{3^1 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3763 := \frac{3^3 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 3^7}{3^1 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 3^1}$$

$$3763 := \frac{3^3 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 3^7}{3^1 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 3^1}$$

$$3764 := \frac{3^7 + 7^0 + 6^5 + 4^7}{3^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3765 := \frac{3^0 + 7^7 + 6^8 + 5^6}{3^0 + 7^1 + 6^2 + 5^4}$$

$$3766 := \frac{-3^8 + 7^5 + 6^4 - 6^5}{3^0 - 7^1 + 6^0 + 6^1}$$

$$3767 := \frac{3^4 + 7^3 - 6^4 + 7^6}{3^0 + 7^0 + 6^2 - 7^1}$$

$$3768 := \frac{3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 8^3}{3^0 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 8^1}$$

$$3768 := \frac{3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6 + 8^3}{3^0 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 8^1}$$

$$3769 := \frac{-3^2 + 7^4 + 6^4 + 9^2}{-3^0 - 7^0 - 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3770 := \frac{-3^6 - 7^2 + 7^6 - 0^0}{3^4 - 7^0 - 7^2 + 0^1}$$

$$3772 := \frac{3^{13} + 7^2 + 7^8 - 2^0}{3^0 - 7^2 - 7^2 + 2^{11}}$$

$$3773 := \frac{-3^6 - 7^0 + 7^5 + 3^8}{3^0 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 3^1}$$

$$3774 := \frac{-3^9 + 7^0 + 7^7 + 4^0}{-3^0 + 7^1 - 7^2 + 4^4}$$

$$3775 := \frac{3^9 - 7^0 + 7^3 + 5^7}{-3^0 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 5^2}$$

$$3776 := \frac{3^{10} - 7^1 - 7^4 - 6^0}{3^0 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 6^1}$$

$$3777 := \frac{3^{11} + 7^2 + 7^4 + 7^5}{3^0 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 7^2}$$

$$3777 := \frac{3^{11} + 7^2 + 7^4 + 7^5}{3^0 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 7^2}$$

$$3778 := \frac{3^{13} - 7^0 - 7^1 + 8^0}{3^4 - 7^0 + 7^3 - 8^0}$$

$$3779 := \frac{3^6 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 9^5}{3^0 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3779 := \frac{3^6 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 9^5}{3^0 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 9^0}$$

$$3780 := \frac{3^3 - 7^3 + 8^4 + 0^1}{-3^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3781 := \frac{3^3 - 7^3 + 8^4 + 1^0}{-3^0 - 7^1 + 8^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3782 := \frac{3^3 + 7^0 + 8^5 + 2^{16}}{3^0 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 2^4}$$

$$3782 := \frac{3^3 + 7^0 + 8^5 + 2^{16}}{3^0 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 2^4}$$

$$3783 := \frac{3^5 + 7^7 + 8^5 + 3^7}{3^4 + 7^0 + 8^2 + 3^4}$$

$$3783 := \frac{3^5 + 7^7 + 8^5 + 3^7}{3^4 + 7^0 + 8^2 + 3^4}$$

$$3784 := \frac{3^2 + 7^1 + 8^8 + 4^5}{3^4 + 7^0 + 8^4 + 4^4}$$

$$3784 := \frac{3^2 + 7^1 + 8^8 + 4^5}{3^4 + 7^0 + 8^4 + 4^4}$$

$$3785 := \frac{3^9 + 7^4 + 8^0 + 5^4}{3^1 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3785 := \frac{3^9 + 7^4 + 8^0 + 5^4}{3^1 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3786 := \frac{3^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 6^4}{3^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$3787 := \frac{3^9 + 7^3 + 8^{10} + 7^3}{3^7 + 7^4 + 8^6 + 7^5}$$

$$3787 := \frac{3^9 + 7^3 + 8^{10} + 7^3}{3^7 + 7^4 + 8^6 + 7^5}$$

$$3788 := \frac{3^3 - 7^3 + 8^1 + 8^4}{-3^0 - 7^1 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$3789 := \frac{3^2 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 9^6}{3^1 + 7^0 + 8^2 + 9^2}$$

$$3789 := \frac{3^2 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 9^6}{3^1 + 7^0 + 8^2 + 9^2}$$

$$3792 := \frac{3^9 + 7^1 - 9^3 - 2^0}{3^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 3793 := \frac{3^0 + 7^5 + 9^5 + 3^1}{3^0 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 3^2} & 3812 := \frac{-3^3 + 8^4 - 1^0 - 2^8}{-3^0 - 8^0 + 1^0 + 2^1} & 3828 := \frac{3^3 + 8^0 + 2^{20} + 8^4}{3^1 + 8^1 + 2^8 + 8^1} \\
 3793 := \frac{3^0 + 7^5 + 9^5 + 3^1}{3^0 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 3^2} & 3814 := \frac{-3^3 + 8^4 + 1^0 - 4^4}{-3^0 - 8^0 - 1^0 + 4^1} & 3828 := \frac{3^3 + 8^0 + 2^{20} + 8^4}{3^1 + 8^1 + 2^8 + 8^1} \\
 3794 := \frac{-3^7 + 7^2 + 9^5 - 4^0}{3^0 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 4^1} & 3816 := \frac{-3^5 + 8^4 - 1^0 - 6^2}{-3^1 - 8^0 - 1^0 + 6^1} & 3829 := \frac{3^2 + 8^4 + 2^{19} + 9^1}{3^0 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 9^0} \\
 3795 := \frac{3^3 + 7^6 + 9^7 + 5^9}{3^6 + 7^3 + 9^3 + 5^1} & 3817 := \frac{-3^4 + 8^7 + 1^0 - 7^5}{3^3 + 8^3 - 1^0 + 7^1} & 3829 := \frac{3^2 + 8^4 + 2^{19} + 9^1}{3^0 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 9^0} \\
 3795 := \frac{3^3 + 7^6 + 9^7 + 5^9}{3^6 + 7^3 + 9^3 + 5^1} & 3820 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^1 + 2^{18} + 0^0}{3^4 + 8^0 + 2^5 + 0^0} & 3831 := \frac{3^2 + 8^6 + 3^7 - 1^0}{3^0 + 8^2 + 3^1 + 1^0} \\
 3796 := \frac{-3^9 + 7^6 + 9^3 + 6^0}{3^2 + 7^1 + 9^1 + 6^0} & 3820 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^1 + 2^{18} + 0^0}{3^4 + 8^0 + 2^5 + 0^0} & 3832 := \frac{3^0 + 8^4 - 3^2 - 2^8}{-3^0 - 8^0 + 3^0 + 2^1} \\
 3797 := \frac{-3^5 - 7^3 + 9^4 + 7^5}{3^1 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 7^0} & 3821 := \frac{-3^9 + 8^5 + 2^{15} - 1^0}{3^0 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 1^0} & 3833 := \frac{-3^1 - 8^3 - 3^1 + 3^9}{-3^0 + 8^1 - 3^0 - 3^0} \\
 3798 := \frac{3^9 + 7^3 + 9^4 - 8^0}{-3^0 - 7^0 + 9^0 + 8^1} & 3822 := \frac{3^0 + 8^7 + 2^0 + 2^{17}}{3^1 + 8^2 + 2^2 + 2^9} & 3834 := \frac{3^0 + 8^2 + 3^3 + 4^{11}}{3^1 + 8^2 + 3^1 + 4^5} \\
 3799 := \frac{3^{11} - 7^4 - 9^0 + 9^1}{3^3 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 9^1} & 3822 := \frac{3^0 + 8^7 + 2^0 + 2^{17}}{3^1 + 8^2 + 2^2 + 2^9} & 3834 := \frac{3^0 + 8^2 + 3^3 + 4^{11}}{3^1 + 8^2 + 3^1 + 4^5} \\
 3802 := \frac{3^6 + 8^4 + 0^0 - 2^{10}}{-3^0 - 8^0 + 0^0 + 2^1} & 3823 := \frac{3^3 + 8^3 + 2^{13} + 3^8}{3^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 3^0} & 3835 := \frac{-3^3 + 8^1 + 3^6 + 5^5}{-3^0 + 8^1 - 3^0 - 5^1} \\
 3803 := \frac{3^6 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 3^6}{-3^0 + 8^0 + 0^1 + 3^2} & 3823 := \frac{3^3 + 8^3 + 2^{13} + 3^8}{3^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 3^0} & 3836 := \frac{3^0 + 8^2 + 3^3 + 6^7}{3^2 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 6^2} \\
 3804 := \frac{3^9 + 8^6 + 0^0 + 4^9}{3^4 - 8^0 - 0^0 + 4^3} & 3824 := \frac{3^8 - 8^0 + 2^6 + 4^5}{-3^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 4^0} & 3836 := \frac{3^0 + 8^2 + 3^3 + 6^7}{3^2 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 6^2} \\
 3805 := \frac{-3^1 + 8^6 - 0^0 + 5^6}{3^1 + 8^2 + 0^0 + 5^1} & 3825 := \frac{3^8 + 8^7 + 2^5 + 5^1}{3^0 + 8^3 + 2^5 + 5^1} & 3837 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^1 + 3^{11} + 7^6}{3^0 + 8^2 + 3^2 + 7^2} \\
 3806 := \frac{-3^2 + 8^7 - 0^0 - 6^2}{3^1 + 8^3 + 0^1 + 6^2} & 3825 := \frac{3^8 + 8^7 + 2^5 + 5^1}{3^0 + 8^3 + 2^5 + 5^1} & 3837 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^1 + 3^{11} + 7^6}{3^0 + 8^2 + 3^2 + 7^2} \\
 3807 := \frac{3^{10} + 8^6 + 0^0 + 7^4}{3^3 + 8^1 + 0^0 + 7^2} & 3826 := \frac{3^{10} + 8^0 + 2^{15} + 6^1}{3^0 + 8^0 + 2^4 + 6^1} & 3838 := \frac{-3^5 + 8^1 + 3^9 - 8^4}{3^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 8^0} \\
 3807 := \frac{3^{10} + 8^6 + 0^0 + 7^4}{3^3 + 8^1 + 0^0 + 7^2} & 3826 := \frac{3^{10} + 8^0 + 2^{15} + 6^1}{3^0 + 8^0 + 2^4 + 6^1} & 3839 := \frac{-3^9 - 8^2 + 3^{11} - 9^0}{-3^1 + 8^1 + 3^3 + 9^1} \\
 3808 := \frac{-3^8 + 8^0 + 0^1 + 8^7}{-3^3 + 8^2 + 0^1 + 8^3} & 3827 := \frac{3^4 + 8^4 + 2^{14} + 7^4}{3^1 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 7^0} & 3840 := \frac{-3^0 + 8^4 - 4^4 + 0^0}{-3^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 0^1} \\
 3809 := \frac{-3^{13} - 8^3 - 0^0 + 9^7}{3^5 + 8^3 + 0^0 + 9^2} & 3827 := \frac{3^4 + 8^4 + 2^{14} + 7^4}{3^1 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 7^0} & 3841 := \frac{3^1 + 8^2 + 4^{11} + 1^0}{3^1 + 8^2 + 4^5 + 1^0}
 \end{array}$$

$$3841 := \frac{3^1 + 8^2 + 4^{11} + 1^0}{3^1 + 8^2 + 4^5 + 1^0}$$

$$3842 := \frac{3^0 + 8^0 - 4^4 + 2^{12}}{-3^0 - 8^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3843 := \frac{3^1 + 8^7 + 4^2 + 3^{12}}{3^3 + 8^3 + 4^3 + 3^4}$$

$$3843 := \frac{3^1 + 8^7 + 4^2 + 3^{12}}{3^3 + 8^3 + 4^3 + 3^4}$$

$$3844 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^3 + 4^0 + 4^{10}}{3^5 + 8^1 + 4^1 + 4^3}$$

$$3844 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^3 + 4^0 + 4^{10}}{3^5 + 8^1 + 4^1 + 4^3}$$

$$3845 := \frac{3^9 + 8^1 + 4^{11} + 5^3}{3^1 + 8^2 + 4^5 + 5^1}$$

$$3845 := \frac{3^9 + 8^1 + 4^{11} + 5^3}{3^1 + 8^2 + 4^5 + 5^1}$$

$$3846 := \frac{-3^5 - 8^0 + 4^6 - 6^1}{-3^0 - 8^0 + 4^1 - 6^0}$$

$$3847 := \frac{3^{10} + 8^1 + 4^4 + 7^6}{3^3 + 8^1 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3847 := \frac{3^{10} + 8^1 + 4^4 + 7^6}{3^3 + 8^1 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3848 := \frac{3^1 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 8^7}{3^2 + 8^1 + 4^2 + 8^3}$$

$$3848 := \frac{3^1 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 8^7}{3^2 + 8^1 + 4^2 + 8^3}$$

$$3849 := \frac{3^3 + 8^7 + 4^6 + 9^6}{3^3 + 8^3 + 4^3 + 9^2}$$

$$3849 := \frac{3^3 + 8^7 + 4^6 + 9^6}{3^3 + 8^3 + 4^3 + 9^2}$$

$$3850 := \frac{-3^3 + 8^7 + 5^7 + 0^1}{3^3 + 8^3 + 5^2 + 0^0}$$

$$3851 := \frac{-3^5 + 8^4 - 5^0 - 1^0}{-3^0 + 8^1 - 5^1 - 1^0}$$

$$3852 := \frac{3^7 + 8^2 + 5^4 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3852 := \frac{3^7 + 8^2 + 5^4 + 2^{14}}{3^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3853 := \frac{3^1 + 8^1 + 5^9 + 3^{15}}{3^0 + 8^4 + 5^3 + 3^2}$$

$$3853 := \frac{3^1 + 8^1 + 5^9 + 3^{15}}{3^0 + 8^4 + 5^3 + 3^2}$$

$$3854 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^1 + 5^3 + 4^1}{3^2 + 8^1 + 5^2 + 4^1}$$

$$3854 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^1 + 5^3 + 4^1}{3^2 + 8^1 + 5^2 + 4^1}$$

$$3855 := \frac{3^{15} + 8^1 + 5^3 + 5^5}{3^4 + 8^3 + 5^1 + 5^5}$$

$$3855 := \frac{3^{15} + 8^1 + 5^3 + 5^5}{3^4 + 8^3 + 5^1 + 5^5}$$

$$3856 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^1 + 5^1 + 6^3}{3^0 + 8^1 + 5^0 + 6^2}$$

$$3857 := \frac{-3^5 + 8^4 + 5^1 - 7^0}{3^0 - 8^1 + 5^0 + 7^1}$$

$$3858 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^2 + 5^6 + 8^2}{3^2 + 8^1 + 5^2 + 8^1}$$

$$3858 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^2 + 5^6 + 8^2}{3^2 + 8^1 + 5^2 + 8^1}$$

$$3859 := \frac{-3^1 + 8^1 + 5^5 + 9^3}{-3^0 - 8^1 + 5^0 + 9^1}$$

$$3860 := \frac{-3^5 + 8^4 + 6^1 + 0^0}{-3^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3861 := \frac{3^2 - 8^2 + 6^5 + 1^0}{-3^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$3862 := \frac{3^4 + 8^0 + 6^2 + 2^{16}}{3^0 + 8^1 + 6^1 + 2^1}$$

$$3862 := \frac{3^4 + 8^0 + 6^2 + 2^{16}}{3^0 + 8^1 + 6^1 + 2^1}$$

$$3863 := \frac{3^1 + 8^3 + 6^2 + 3^{11}}{3^0 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 3^0}$$

$$3863 := \frac{3^1 + 8^3 + 6^2 + 3^{11}}{3^0 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 3^0}$$

$$3864 := \frac{3^{10} - 8^2 - 6^0 - 4^5}{3^2 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3865 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^3}{3^0 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 5^0}$$

$$3865 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^3}{3^0 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 5^0}$$

$$3866 := \frac{3^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 6^4}{3^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 6^1}$$

$$3866 := \frac{3^6 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 6^4}{3^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 6^1}$$

$$3867 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^3 + 6^3 + 7^1}{3^0 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$3867 := \frac{3^{11} + 8^3 + 6^3 + 7^1}{3^0 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$3868 := \frac{3^{12} - 8^0 - 6^4 - 8^4}{3^2 + 8^2 - 6^0 + 8^2}$$

$$3869 := \frac{3^8 + 8^2 + 6^6 + 9^7}{3^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 9^3}$$

$$3869 := \frac{3^8 + 8^2 + 6^6 + 9^7}{3^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 9^3}$$

$$3870 := \frac{3^{13} - 8^4 + 7^3 + 0^1}{3^1 + 8^2 + 7^3 + 0^0}$$

$$3872 := \frac{3^6 + 8^5 + 7^5 + 2^5}{3^0 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3872 := \frac{3^6 + 8^5 + 7^5 + 2^5}{3^0 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3873 := \frac{3^{10} + 8^1 + 7^2 + 3^{11}}{3^0 + 8^1 + 7^2 + 3^1}$$

$$3873 := \frac{3^{10} + 8^1 + 7^2 + 3^{11}}{3^0 + 8^1 + 7^2 + 3^1}$$

$$3874 := \frac{3^9 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 4^8}{3^1 + 8^1 + 7^1 + 4^1}$$

$$3874 := \frac{3^9 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 4^8}{3^1 + 8^1 + 7^1 + 4^1}$$

$$3875 := \frac{3^8 + 8^4 + 7^3 + 5^7}{3^1 + 8^1 + 7^1 + 5^1}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 3875 := \frac{3^8 + 8^4 + 7^3 + 5^7}{3^1 + 8^1 + 7^1 + 5^1} & 3889 := \frac{3^7 - 8^1 + 8^7 + 9^3}{3^3 - 8^1 + 8^3 + 9^1} & 3917 := \frac{-3^8 + 9^6 - 1^0 - 7^0}{3^1 + 9^2 + 1^0 + 7^2} \\
 3876 := \frac{3^{10} + 8^5 + 7^3 + 6^7}{3^1 + 8^1 + 7^2 + 6^2} & 3892 := \frac{3^7 + 8^2 + 9^1 + 2^{15}}{3^1 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 2^2} & 3920 := \frac{3^9 - 9^2 - 2^0 - 0^0}{3^0 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 0^0} \\
 3876 := \frac{3^{10} + 8^5 + 7^3 + 6^7}{3^1 + 8^1 + 7^2 + 6^2} & 3892 := \frac{3^7 + 8^2 + 9^1 + 2^{15}}{3^1 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 2^2} & 3921 := \frac{3^9 - 9^2 + 2^1 + 1^0}{3^0 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 1^0} \\
 3877 := \frac{3^7 + 8^1 + 7^3 + 7^6}{3^2 + 8^1 + 7^1 + 7^1} & 3893 := \frac{-3^0 + 8^3 - 9^3 + 3^9}{-3^0 + 8^1 - 9^0 - 3^0} & 3922 := \frac{3^7 + 9^2 + 2^3 + 2^{17}}{3^0 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 2^4} \\
 3877 := \frac{3^7 + 8^1 + 7^3 + 7^6}{3^2 + 8^1 + 7^1 + 7^1} & 3894 := \frac{3^7 + 8^3 + 9^6 + 4^8}{3^0 + 8^1 + 9^2 + 4^3} & 3922 := \frac{3^7 + 9^2 + 2^3 + 2^{17}}{3^0 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 2^4} \\
 3878 := \frac{3^5 + 8^1 + 7^6 + 8^6}{3^4 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 8^1} & 3894 := \frac{3^7 + 8^3 + 9^6 + 4^8}{3^0 + 8^1 + 9^2 + 4^3} & 3923 := \frac{3^5 + 9^6 + 2^3 + 3^{12}}{3^1 + 9^1 + 2^4 + 3^5} \\
 3878 := \frac{3^5 + 8^1 + 7^6 + 8^6}{3^4 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 8^1} & 3895 := \frac{3^5 + 8^4 + 9^6 + 5^9}{3^0 + 8^3 + 9^0 + 5^3} & 3923 := \frac{3^5 + 9^6 + 2^3 + 3^{12}}{3^1 + 9^1 + 2^4 + 3^5} \\
 3879 := \frac{3^3 + 8^7 + 7^6 + 9^2}{3^0 + 8^3 + 7^2 + 9^1} & 3895 := \frac{3^5 + 8^4 + 9^6 + 5^9}{3^0 + 8^3 + 9^0 + 5^3} & 3924 := \frac{3^{11} + 9^4 + 2^5 + 4^7}{3^2 + 9^1 + 2^5 + 4^0} \\
 3879 := \frac{3^3 + 8^7 + 7^6 + 9^2}{3^0 + 8^3 + 7^2 + 9^1} & 3896 := \frac{-3^0 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 6^5}{-3^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 6^0} & 3924 := \frac{3^{11} + 9^4 + 2^5 + 4^7}{3^2 + 9^1 + 2^5 + 4^0} \\
 3880 := \frac{-3^6 + 8^3 + 8^4 + 0^0}{-3^0 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 0^1} & 3897 := \frac{3^9 + 8^2 + 9^2 - 7^3}{-3^0 + 8^1 - 9^0 - 7^0} & 3925 := \frac{3^9 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 5^6}{3^0 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 5^1} \\
 3881 := \frac{3^9 - 8^2 - 8^4 + 1^0}{3^0 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 1^0} & 3898 := \frac{3^9 + 8^2 + 9^4 + 8^6}{3^0 + 8^1 + 9^0 + 8^2} & 3925 := \frac{3^9 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 5^6}{3^0 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 5^1} \\
 3882 := \frac{3^5 + 8^0 + 8^4 + 2^{16}}{3^0 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 2^3} & 3898 := \frac{3^9 + 8^2 + 9^4 + 8^6}{3^0 + 8^1 + 9^0 + 8^2} & 3926 := \frac{3^7 + 9^1 + 2^{17} + 6^3}{3^1 + 9^1 + 2^4 + 6^1} \\
 3882 := \frac{3^5 + 8^0 + 8^4 + 2^{16}}{3^0 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 2^3} & 3899 := \frac{3^{13} - 8^4 + 9^0 + 9^5}{3^0 + 8^3 - 9^1 - 9^2} & 3926 := \frac{3^7 + 9^1 + 2^{17} + 6^3}{3^1 + 9^1 + 2^4 + 6^1} \\
 3883 := \frac{3^2 - 8^2 - 8^4 + 3^9}{3^0 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 3^0} & 3902 := \frac{3^{13} - 9^0 + 0^1 - 2^{17}}{3^4 - 9^3 - 0^0 + 2^{10}} & 3927 := \frac{3^9 + 9^2 + 2^5 + 7^6}{3^0 + 9^0 + 2^5 + 7^0} \\
 3884 := \frac{3^9 + 8^0 - 8^1 - 4^4}{-3^0 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 4^1} & 3905 := \frac{-3^1 - 9^0 - 0^0 + 5^6}{3^0 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 5^0} & 3927 := \frac{3^9 + 9^2 + 2^5 + 7^6}{3^0 + 9^0 + 2^5 + 7^0} \\
 3885 := \frac{-3^1 - 8^4 - 8^4 + 5^7}{3^0 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 5^0} & 3906 := \frac{3^3 + 9^1 + 0^1 + 6^5}{-3^0 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 6^0} & 3928 := \frac{-3^4 + 9^4 + 2^5 + 8^5}{-3^0 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 8^1} \\
 3886 := \frac{3^1 + 8^0 - 8^1 + 6^5}{-3^0 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 6^0} & 3913 := \frac{-3^0 + 9^3 - 1^0 + 3^{12}}{3^3 + 9^2 + 1^0 + 3^3} & 3929 := \frac{3^{13} + 9^3 + 2^3 + 9^5}{3^1 + 9^2 + 2^8 + 9^2} \\
 3887 := \frac{3^7 - 8^1 + 8^6 - 7^1}{3^1 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 7^2} & 3915 := \frac{3^3 + 9^1 - 1^0 + 5^6}{3^0 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 5^0} & 3929 := \frac{3^{13} + 9^3 + 2^3 + 9^5}{3^1 + 9^2 + 2^8 + 9^2}
 \end{array}$$

$$3933 := \frac{-3^2 + 9^5 - 3^3 - 3^9}{3^1 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 3^1}$$

$$3934 := \frac{-3^1 - 9^1 + 3^9 - 4^0}{-3^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3935 := \frac{3^2 + 9^3 + 3^{11} + 5^5}{3^1 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 5^2}$$

$$3935 := \frac{3^2 + 9^3 + 3^{11} + 5^5}{3^1 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 5^2}$$

$$3936 := \frac{-3^0 - 9^0 + 3^9 - 6^0}{-3^0 - 9^0 + 3^0 + 6^1}$$

$$3937 := \frac{3^0 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 7^1}{3^0 + 9^1 + 3^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3937 := \frac{3^0 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 7^1}{3^0 + 9^1 + 3^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3938 := \frac{3^3 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 8^0}{3^0 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 8^0}$$

$$3938 := \frac{3^3 + 9^5 + 3^9 + 8^0}{3^0 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 8^0}$$

$$3939 := \frac{-3^2 + 9^2 + 3^{10} + 9^5}{3^0 + 9^0 + 3^3 + 9^0}$$

$$3940 := \frac{3^9 + 9^0 + 4^2 + 0^1}{3^1 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3941 := \frac{3^0 + 9^5 + 4^3 + 1^0}{3^0 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3942 := \frac{3^9 + 9^1 + 4^2 + 2^1}{3^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3943 := \frac{3^2 + 9^6 + 4^7 + 3^5}{3^3 + 9^2 + 4^1 + 3^3}$$

$$3944 := \frac{3^7 + 9^3 + 4^1 + 4^5}{-3^0 - 9^0 - 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3945 := \frac{3^3 + 9^3 + 4^3 + 5^5}{-3^0 - 9^0 + 4^1 - 5^0}$$

$$3946 := \frac{3^0 + 9^5 + 4^4 + 6^5}{3^0 + 9^1 + 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$3947 := \frac{3^7 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 7^1}{-3^0 - 9^0 + 4^1 - 7^0}$$

$$3948 := \frac{3^1 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 8^5}{3^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 8^1}$$

$$3949 := \frac{3^7 + 9^1 + 4^5 + 9^3}{-3^0 - 9^0 + 4^1 - 9^0}$$

$$3950 := \frac{3^3 + 9^5 - 5^6 - 0^0}{3^0 + 9^1 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3951 := \frac{-3^7 + 9^6 - 5^6 + 1^0}{3^1 + 9^0 + 5^3 + 1^0}$$

$$3952 := \frac{3^9 + 9^2 - 5^1 + 2^0}{3^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$3953 := \frac{-3^2 + 9^3 + 5^4 + 3^8}{-3^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$3954 := \frac{3^9 + 9^2 + 5^1 + 4^0}{-3^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3955 := \frac{3^6 + 9^4 - 5^1 + 5^4}{-3^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$3956 := \frac{3^6 - 9^5 + 5^8 - 6^0}{3^0 + 9^2 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$3957 := \frac{3^3 + 9^1 + 5^7 + 7^5}{3^1 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3957 := \frac{3^3 + 9^1 + 5^7 + 7^5}{3^1 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3958 := \frac{3^6 + 9^4 + 5^4 + 8^0}{-3^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$3959 := \frac{3^3 + 9^8 + 5^7 + 9^8}{3^9 + 9^3 + 5^4 + 9^3}$$

$$3959 := \frac{3^3 + 9^8 + 5^7 + 9^8}{3^9 + 9^3 + 5^4 + 9^3}$$

$$3960 := \frac{3^9 + 9^2 + 6^2 + 0^1}{3^1 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3960 := \frac{3^9 + 9^2 + 6^2 + 0^1}{3^1 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3961 := \frac{-3^7 + 9^7 - 6^5 - 1^0}{-3^2 - 9^2 + 6^4 - 1^0}$$

$$3962 := \frac{3^7 + 9^4 + 6^6 + 2^6}{3^1 + 9^0 + 6^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3962 := \frac{3^7 + 9^4 + 6^6 + 2^6}{3^1 + 9^0 + 6^1 + 2^2}$$

$$3963 := \frac{3^5 + 9^3 + 6^3 + 3^{11}}{3^1 + 9^1 + 6^1 + 3^3}$$

$$3963 := \frac{3^5 + 9^3 + 6^3 + 3^{11}}{3^1 + 9^1 + 6^1 + 3^3}$$

$$3964 := \frac{3^{13} + 9^4 + 6^7 + 4^{10}}{3^1 + 9^3 + 6^1 + 4^0}$$

$$3964 := \frac{3^{13} + 9^4 + 6^7 + 4^{10}}{3^1 + 9^3 + 6^1 + 4^0}$$

$$3965 := \frac{3^9 + 9^6 + 6^1 + 5^1}{3^3 + 9^2 + 6^1 + 5^2}$$

$$3965 := \frac{3^9 + 9^6 + 6^1 + 5^1}{3^3 + 9^2 + 6^1 + 5^2}$$

$$3966 := \frac{3^{13} + 9^3 + 6^3 + 6^6}{3^4 + 9^2 + 6^2 + 6^3}$$

$$3966 := \frac{3^{13} + 9^3 + 6^3 + 6^6}{3^4 + 9^2 + 6^2 + 6^3}$$

$$3967 := \frac{3^2 + 9^1 + 6^8 + 7^7}{3^5 + 9^1 + 6^2 + 7^3}$$

$$3967 := \frac{3^2 + 9^1 + 6^8 + 7^7}{3^5 + 9^1 + 6^2 + 7^3}$$

$$3968 := \frac{-3^0 + 9^5 + 6^3 + 8^6}{3^2 + 9^1 - 6^0 + 8^2}$$

$$3969 := \frac{3^6 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 9^5}{3^1 + 9^1 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3969 := \frac{3^6 + 9^3 + 6^6 + 9^5}{3^1 + 9^1 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3969 := \frac{3^4 + 9^4 - 6^4 + 9^4}{-3^1 + 9^1 + 6^1 - 9^1}$$

$$3970 := \frac{-3^{12} + 9^7 + 7^3 - 0^0}{-3^0 + 9^3 + 7^3 + 0^1}$$

$$3971 := \frac{3^{11} + 9^0 + 7^7 + 1^0}{3^5 + 9^0 + 7^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3971 := \frac{3^{11} + 9^0 + 7^7 + 1^0}{3^5 + 9^0 + 7^1 + 1^0}$$

$$3972 := \frac{3^{11} + 9^2 - 7^6 + 2^0}{3^0 + 9^1 + 7^0 + 2^2}$$

$$3973 := \frac{3^6 + 9^5 - 7^0 + 3^9}{3^0 + 9^1 + 7^0 + 3^2}$$

$$3974 := \frac{3^9 + 9^4 - 7^4 + 4^0}{3^1 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$3975 := \frac{3^{11} + 9^3 + 7^6 + 5^7}{3^0 + 9^2 + 7^1 + 5^1}$$

$$3975 := \frac{3^{11} + 9^3 + 7^6 + 5^7}{3^0 + 9^2 + 7^1 + 5^1}$$

$$3976 := \frac{-3^8 + 9^6 - 7^2 + 6^0}{3^0 + 9^2 + 7^2 + 6^0}$$

$$3977 := \frac{3^7 + 9^7 - 7^4 - 7^4}{3^4 + 9^3 + 7^2 + 7^3}$$

$$3978 := \frac{-3^4 + 9^6 - 7^6 + 8^0}{-3^3 + 9^2 + 7^2 + 8^0}$$

$$3979 := \frac{-3^4 - 9^2 + 7^5 - 9^3}{3^0 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$3980 := \frac{3^9 + 9^3 - 8^3 + 0^1}{3^1 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$3981 := \frac{3^6 + 9^5 - 8^2 + 1^0}{-3^0 + 9^1 + 8^1 - 1^0}$$

$$3982 := \frac{3^9 + 9^2 + 8^4 + 2^5}{3^1 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3982 := \frac{3^9 + 9^2 + 8^4 + 2^5}{3^1 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$3983 := \frac{-3^3 + 9^6 + 8^3 - 3^7}{-3^1 - 9^1 + 8^2 + 3^4}$$

$$3984 := \frac{-3^3 - 9^2 + 8^4 - 4^1}{-3^0 - 9^0 - 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$3985 := \frac{3^9 - 9^1 - 8^2 - 5^6}{-3^0 - 9^0 + 8^1 - 5^1}$$

$$3986 := \frac{3^2 + 9^5 + 8^7 + 6^3}{3^3 + 9^0 + 8^3 + 6^0}$$

$$3986 := \frac{3^2 + 9^5 + 8^7 + 6^3}{3^3 + 9^0 + 8^3 + 6^0}$$

$$3987 := \frac{-3^3 - 9^2 + 8^4 - 7^0}{3^0 + 9^0 - 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$3988 := \frac{3^9 + 9^3 + 8^2 + 8^7}{3^2 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 8^3}$$

$$3988 := \frac{3^9 + 9^3 + 8^2 + 8^7}{3^2 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 8^3}$$

$$3989 := \frac{-3^3 + 9^0 + 8^4 - 9^2}{-3^0 + 9^0 - 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$3993 := \frac{3^1 - 9^3 - 9^3 + 3^{11}}{-3^0 + 9^1 + 9^1 + 3^3}$$

$$3995 := \frac{-3^1 + 9^1 + 9^5 - 5^5}{3^1 + 9^0 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$3996 := \frac{3^3 - 9^0 + 9^6 + 6^0}{-3^0 - 9^0 - 9^2 + 6^3}$$

$$3997 := \frac{3^9 + 9^2 + 9^5 + 7^8}{3^1 + 9^3 + 9^3 + 7^0}$$

$$3997 := \frac{3^9 + 9^2 + 9^5 + 7^8}{3^1 + 9^3 + 9^3 + 7^0}$$

$$4013 := \frac{4^6 - 0^0 - 1^0 - 3^4}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4016 := \frac{4^4 - 0^0 + 1^0 + 6^5}{-4^0 + 0^0 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4023 := \frac{4^8 + 0^1 + 2^7 + 3^{10}}{4^0 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 3^3}$$

$$4023 := \frac{4^8 + 0^1 + 2^7 + 3^{10}}{4^0 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 3^3}$$

$$4024 := \frac{-4^3 + 0^1 - 2^3 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 0^0 - 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4025 := \frac{-4^2 - 0^0 + 2^{13} - 5^3}{-4^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4026 := \frac{-4^3 + 0^1 + 2^{12} - 6^1}{-4^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$4027 := \frac{4^6 + 0^0 + 2^{20} + 7^4}{4^1 + 0^0 + 2^8 + 7^0}$$

$$4027 := \frac{4^6 + 0^0 + 2^{20} + 7^4}{4^1 + 0^0 + 2^8 + 7^0}$$

$$4028 := \frac{-4^1 + 0^1 - 2^6 + 8^4}{-4^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$4029 := \frac{-4^7 + 0^1 + 2^{18} + 9^1}{-4^0 - 0^0 + 2^6 - 9^0}$$

$$4032 := \frac{4^1 + 0^0 + 3^{11} + 2^8}{4^0 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 2^4}$$

$$4032 := \frac{4^1 + 0^0 + 3^{11} + 2^8}{4^0 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 2^4}$$

$$4033 := \frac{4^{10} + 0^1 + 3^0 + 3^1}{4^2 + 0^1 + 3^0 + 3^5}$$

$$4033 := \frac{4^{10} + 0^1 + 3^0 + 3^1}{4^2 + 0^1 + 3^0 + 3^5}$$

$$4034 := \frac{4^6 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 4^9}{4^0 + 0^1 + 3^0 + 4^3}$$

$$4034 := \frac{4^6 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 4^9}{4^0 + 0^1 + 3^0 + 4^3}$$

$$4035 := \frac{4^2 + 0^1 + 3^{10} + 5^7}{4^0 + 0^0 + 3^3 + 5^1}$$

$$4035 := \frac{4^2 + 0^1 + 3^{10} + 5^7}{4^0 + 0^0 + 3^3 + 5^1}$$

$$4036 := \frac{4^5 + 0^0 - 3^6 + 6^5}{-4^0 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4037 := \frac{4^6 - 0^0 - 3^2 - 7^2}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4038 := \frac{-4^1 - 0^0 + 3^9 + 8^3}{4^0 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 8^0}$$

$$4039 := \frac{4^5 + 0^1 - 3^9 + 9^5}{-4^0 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$4041 := \frac{4^4 - 0^0 + 4^{11} - 1^0}{4^2 - 0^0 + 4^5 - 1^0}$$

$$4045 := \frac{-4^0 + 0^1 + 4^{10} + 5^5}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 4^4 + 5^1}$$

$$4046 := \frac{4^2 + 0^1 + 4^7 - 6^3}{4^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4047 := \frac{-4^0 + 0^0 + 4^6 - 7^2}{-4^0 - 0^0 + 4^1 - 7^0}$$

$$4048 := \frac{4^2 + 0^1 - 4^3 + 8^4}{-4^0 - 0^0 + 4^1 - 8^0}$$

$$4052 := \frac{-4^3 + 0^0 - 5^2 + 2^{13}}{-4^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4053 := \frac{-4^1 - 0^0 - 5^6 + 3^9}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4054 := \frac{-4^2 - 0^0 - 5^2 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 0^0 - 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4056 := \frac{4^6 + 0^0 - 5^1 - 6^2}{-4^0 + 0^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$4057 := \frac{4^8 + 0^1 - 5^4 + 7^0}{4^1 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 7^1}$$

$$4058 := \frac{-4^3 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 8^4}{-4^0 - 0^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$4059 := \frac{4^{10} + 0^1 - 5^4 - 9^3}{4^4 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4060 := \frac{4^6 - 0^0 - 6^2 + 0^0}{-4^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$4061 := \frac{4^6 + 0^1 - 6^2 + 1^0}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4062 := \frac{4^0 + 0^0 - 6^2 + 2^{12}}{-4^0 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4063 := \frac{4^{10} + 0^0 + 6^5 + 3^3}{4^2 + 0^0 + 6^3 + 3^3}$$

$$4063 := \frac{4^{10} + 0^0 + 6^5 + 3^3}{4^2 + 0^0 + 6^3 + 3^3}$$

$$4064 := \frac{4^1 + 0^1 - 6^2 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 0^0 - 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4065 := \frac{4^6 + 0^1 - 6^1 - 5^2}{4^0 + 0^0 - 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$4066 := \frac{4^9 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 6^6}{4^1 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 6^2}$$

$$4066 := \frac{4^9 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 6^6}{4^1 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 6^2}$$

$$4067 := \frac{4^6 + 0^1 - 6^2 + 7^1}{-4^0 + 0^0 - 6^1 + 7^1}$$

$$4068 := \frac{-4^3 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 8^4}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4069 := \frac{4^6 + 0^1 - 6^2 + 9^1}{-4^0 - 0^0 - 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$4072 := \frac{-4^2 - 0^0 - 7^1 + 2^{12}}{-4^0 - 0^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4073 := \frac{4^6 - 0^0 - 7^2 + 3^3}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4074 := \frac{-4^2 + 0^0 - 7^1 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 0^0 - 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4075 := \frac{-4^9 + 0^0 + 7^7 - 5^5}{4^1 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 5^3}$$

$$4076 := \frac{-4^4 + 0^0 - 7^2 + 6^8}{4^3 - 0^0 + 7^3 + 6^1}$$

$$4078 := \frac{-4^2 - 0^0 - 7^0 + 8^4}{-4^0 + 0^0 - 7^1 + 8^1}$$

$$4079 := \frac{4^6 - 0^0 - 7^1 - 9^1}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4080 := \frac{-4^2 - 0^0 + 8^4 + 0^0}{-4^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$4081 := \frac{-4^2 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 1^0}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4082 := \frac{4^0 + 0^0 + 8^4 - 2^4}{-4^0 - 0^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4083 := \frac{4^{11} + 0^0 + 8^6 + 3^7}{4^5 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 3^1}$$

$$4083 := \frac{4^{11} + 0^0 + 8^6 + 3^7}{4^5 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 3^1}$$

$$4084 := \frac{-4^1 + 0^1 - 8^1 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 0^0 - 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4085 := \frac{4^6 + 0^6 + 8^6 + 5^6}{4^1 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 5^0}$$

$$4085 := \frac{4^6 + 0^6 + 8^6 + 5^6}{4^1 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 5^0}$$

$$4086 := \frac{-4^1 + 0^1 + 8^4 - 6^1}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4087 := \frac{-4^0 - 0^0 + 8^4 - 7^1}{4^0 + 0^0 - 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$4088 := \frac{-4^0 + 0^0 - 8^1 + 8^4}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4089 := \frac{4^3 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 9^6}{4^3 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 9^0}$$

$$4089 := \frac{4^3 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 9^6}{4^3 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 9^0}$$

$$4091 := \frac{4^8 + 0^1 - 9^2 + 1^0}{4^2 + 0^1 - 9^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4092 := \frac{-4^1 - 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^{12}}{-4^0 - 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4093 := \frac{4^6 - 0^0 - 9^0 - 3^0}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4094 := \frac{-4^0 + 0^1 - 9^0 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 0^0 - 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4095 := \frac{4^6 - 0^0 - 9^0 + 5^0}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4096 := \frac{4^6 + 0^1 - 9^0 + 6^0}{-4^0 - 0^0 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$4097 := \frac{4^1 + 0^0 + 9^5 + 7^4}{4^1 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 7^0}$$

$$4097 := \frac{4^1 + 0^0 + 9^5 + 7^4}{4^1 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 7^0}$$

$$4098 := \frac{4^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 8^4}{4^0 + 0^0 - 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$4099 := \frac{4^6 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}{-4^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4102 := \frac{4^1 + 1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{12}}{-4^0 - 1^0 + 0^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4103 := \frac{4^7 + 1^0 + 0^1 + 3^3}{4^0 + 1^0 + 0^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4103 := \frac{4^7 + 1^0 + 0^1 + 3^3}{4^0 + 1^0 + 0^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4104 := \frac{-4^2 - 1^0 + 0^0 + 4^{11}}{-4^0 - 1^0 + 0^1 + 4^5}$$

$$4112 := \frac{4^2 - 1^0 + 1^0 + 2^{12}}{-4^0 - 1^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4114 := \frac{4^2 + 1^0 + 1^0 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 1^0 - 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4123 := \frac{-4^0 + 1^0 + 2^{12} + 3^3}{-4^0 - 1^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$4125 := \frac{4^3 - 1^0 + 2^{13} - 5^1}{-4^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4126 := \frac{4^6 - 1^0 + 2^5 - 6^0}{-4^0 - 1^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$4127 := \frac{4^3 - 1^0 + 2^{13} - 7^0}{-4^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4128 := \frac{-4^0 + 1^0 + 2^5 + 8^4}{-4^0 - 1^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$4129 := \frac{4^3 + 1^0 + 2^{13} + 9^0}{-4^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4132 := \frac{4^2 + 1^0 + 3^{11} + 2^9}{4^0 + 1^0 + 3^2 + 2^5}$$

$$4133 := \frac{4^{10} + 1^0 + 3^7 + 3^9}{4^4 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4134 := \frac{4^5 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 4^6}{4^0 + 1^0 + 3^1 + 4^0}$$

$$4134 := \frac{4^5 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 4^6}{4^0 + 1^0 + 3^1 + 4^0}$$

$$4135 := \frac{-4^4 - 1^0 + 3^{11} - 5^6}{4^1 + 1^0 + 3^2 + 5^2}$$

$$4136 := \frac{4^6 + 1^0 + 3^1 + 6^2}{-4^0 - 1^0 - 3^1 + 6^1}$$

$$4137 := \frac{4^6 + 1^0 - 3^2 + 7^2}{4^1 - 1^0 - 3^0 - 7^0}$$

$$4138 := \frac{4^2 - 1^0 + 3^3 + 8^4}{4^0 + 1^0 - 3^2 + 8^1}$$

$$4139 := \frac{4^{10} + 1^0 - 3^9 - 9^4}{4^1 - 1^0 + 3^5 + 9^0}$$

$$4143 := \frac{-4^0 - 1^0 - 4^9 + 3^{12}}{-4^0 + 1^0 - 4^2 + 3^4}$$

$$4147 := \frac{4^0 + 1^0 + 4^6 + 7^2}{-4^0 - 1^0 + 4^1 - 7^0}$$

$$4150 := \frac{4^5 + 1^5 + 5^5 + 0^5}{-4^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$4151 := \frac{4^5 + 1^5 + 5^5 + 1^5}{4^1 - 1^0 - 5^0 - 1^0}$$

$$4151 := \frac{4^5 + 1^5 + 5^5 + 1^5}{-4^1 + 1^1 + 5^1 - 1^1}$$

$$4152 := \frac{4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 2^1}{-4^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4153 := \frac{4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 3^1}{4^1 - 1^0 - 5^0 - 3^0}$$

$$4154 := \frac{4^1 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 4^5}{-4^0 - 1^0 - 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4155 := \frac{4^5 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 5^5}{4^1 - 1^0 - 5^0 - 5^0}$$

$$4156 := \frac{4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 6^1}{-4^0 + 1^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$4156 := \frac{-4^6 - 1^6 + 5^6 + 6^6}{4^1 - 1^1 + 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$4157 := \frac{4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 7^1}{4^1 - 1^0 - 5^0 - 7^0}$$

$$4158 := \frac{4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 8^1}{-4^0 - 1^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$4159 := \frac{4^5 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 9^1}{4^1 - 1^0 - 5^0 - 9^0}$$

$$4161 := \frac{4^9 - 1^0 - 6^0 + 1^0}{4^3 - 1^0 - 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4162 := \frac{4^3 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 2^{12}}{-4^0 - 1^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4163 := \frac{-4^7 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 3^9}{4^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 3^2}$$

$$4169 := \frac{-4^8 + 1^0 + 6^9 - 9^4}{4^5 - 1^0 + 6^4 + 9^2}$$

$$4172 := \frac{4^4 - 1^0 + 7^2 + 2^{14}}{4^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4173 := \frac{4^6 + 1^0 + 7^2 + 3^3}{4^1 - 1^0 - 7^0 - 3^0}$$

$$4174 := \frac{-4^7 - 1^0 + 7^8 + 4^9}{4^3 - 1^0 + 7^4 - 4^5}$$

$$4175 := \frac{-4^9 + 1^0 - 7^5 + 5^9}{4^3 - 1^0 + 7^3 - 5^1}$$

$$4176 := \frac{4^7 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 6^3}{-4^0 + 1^0 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$4177 := \frac{4^{10} - 1^0 - 7^2 - 7^5}{4^4 - 1^0 - 7^0 - 7^1}$$

$$4178 := \frac{4^{10} - 1^0 + 7^5 + 8^1}{4^4 - 1^0 - 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4179 := \frac{4^6 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 9^2}{4^1 - 1^0 - 7^0 - 9^0}$$

$$4183 := \frac{4^{10} - 1^0 - 8^6 - 3^3}{-4^3 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 3^5}$$

$$4186 := \frac{-4^0 - 1^0 + 8^7 + 6^2}{-4^1 - 1^0 + 8^3 - 6^1}$$

$$4187 := \frac{4^1 + 1^0 - 8^2 + 7^5}{4^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4189 := \frac{4^2 - 1^0 + 8^5 + 9^3}{-4^0 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 9^1}$$

$$4192 := \frac{4^2 - 1^0 + 9^2 + 2^{12}}{-4^0 - 1^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4194 := \frac{4^2 + 1^0 + 9^2 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 1^0 - 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4196 := \frac{4^8 - 1^0 + 9^5 + 6^4}{-4^1 - 1^0 - 9^0 + 6^2}$$

$$4197 := \frac{4^6 + 1^0 + 9^2 + 7^5}{4^1 - 1^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4201 := \frac{4^8 + 2^{18} - 0^0 - 1^0}{4^2 + 2^6 - 0^0 - 1^0}$$

$$4203 := \frac{4^{12} + 2^{10} + 0^0 - 3^{15}}{4^3 + 2^9 + 0^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4205 := \frac{-4^2 + 2^{12} + 0^1 + 5^3}{-4^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$4206 := \frac{4^1 + 2^{13} + 0^1 + 6^3}{-4^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4207 := \frac{4^1 + 2^4 + 0^0 + 7^5}{4^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4207 := \frac{4^1 + 2^4 + 0^0 + 7^5}{4^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4208 := \frac{-4^2 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 8^4}{-4^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 8^0}$$

$$4209 := \frac{4^6 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 9^2}{-4^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 9^0}$$

$$4213 := \frac{-4^1 - 2^6 + 1^0 + 3^{10}}{4^1 + 2^3 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4215 := \frac{4^9 - 2^{11} - 1^0 - 5^6}{4^2 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 5^2}$$

$$4216 := \frac{-4^{15} - 2^0 + 1^0 + 6^{12}}{4^9 - 2^9 - 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4217 := \frac{-4^1 + 2^6 + 1^0 + 7^5}{4^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4219 := \frac{4^4 + 2^{13} - 1^0 - 9^1}{-4^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4220 := \frac{-4^1 + 2^7 + 2^{12} + 0^1}{-4^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 0^1}$$

$$4221 := \frac{-4^1 + 2^7 + 2^{12} + 1^0}{-4^0 - 2^0 + 2^1 + 1^0}$$

$$4222 := \frac{-4^0 - 2^0 + 2^7 + 2^{12}}{-4^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4223 := \frac{4^0 + 2^3 + 2^6 + 3^{10}}{4^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 3^2}$$

$$4223 := \frac{4^0 + 2^3 + 2^6 + 3^{10}}{4^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 3^2}$$

$$4224 := \frac{4^4 + 2^7 + 2^7 + 4^7}{4^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4225 := \frac{4^1 + 2^{11} + 2^{11} + 5^3}{-4^0 - 2^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$4226 := \frac{4^7 + 2^1 + 2^9 + 6^1}{4^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4227 := \frac{4^3 + 2^1 + 2^{17} + 7^5}{4^0 + 2^0 + 2^5 + 7^0}$$

$$4228 := \frac{4^2 + 2^{13} + 2^{13} + 8^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4229 := \frac{4^2 + 2^1 + 2^{17} + 9^1}{4^1 + 2^1 + 2^4 + 9^1}$$

$$4230 := \frac{4^0 + 2^9 + 3^{11} + 0^1}{4^0 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 0^1}$$

$$4230 := \frac{4^0 + 2^9 + 3^{11} + 0^1}{4^0 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 0^1}$$

$$4231 := \frac{4^7 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 1^0}{4^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4231 := \frac{4^7 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 1^0}{4^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4232 := \frac{-4^0 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 2^{11}}{-4^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4233 := \frac{4^7 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 3^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4233 := \frac{4^7 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 3^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4234 := \frac{4^0 + 2^4 + 3^{12} + 4^8}{4^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^3}$$

$$4235 := \frac{4^8 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^1}{4^0 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 5^1}$$

$$4235 := \frac{4^8 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^1}{4^0 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 5^1}$$

$$4236 := \frac{4^0 + 2^{17} + 3^3 + 6^3}{4^0 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 6^0}$$

$$4236 := \frac{4^0 + 2^{17} + 3^3 + 6^3}{4^0 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 6^0}$$

$$4237 := \frac{4^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^5}{4^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4237 := \frac{4^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^5}{4^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4238 := \frac{4^{10} + 2^{13} + 3^9 + 8^0}{4^0 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 8^1}$$

$$4238 := \frac{4^{10} + 2^{13} + 3^9 + 8^0}{4^0 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 8^1}$$

$$4239 := \frac{4^2 + 2^{13} + 3^7 + 9^4}{4^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4239 := \frac{4^2 + 2^{13} + 3^7 + 9^4}{4^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4240 := \frac{4^3 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 0^1}{4^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$4241 := \frac{4^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 1^0}{-4^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 - 1^0}$$

$$4242 := \frac{4^3 + 2^3 + 4^7 + 2^9}{4^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4243 := \frac{4^1 + 2^{11} + 4^1 + 3^7}{-4^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 - 3^0}$$

$$4244 := \frac{4^2 + 2^9 + 4^3 + 4^7}{4^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4245 := \frac{4^7 + 2^{17} + 4^7 + 5^7}{4^1 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$4246 := \frac{4^4 + 2^7 + 4^7 + 6^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4247 := \frac{4^7 + 2^{17} + 4^{10} + 7^8}{4^2 + 2^8 + 4^5 + 7^3}$$

$$4248 := \frac{4^3 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 8^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4249 := \frac{4^7 + 2^{19} + 4^7 + 9^5}{4^1 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 9^1}$$

$$4250 := \frac{4^6 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 0^0}{-4^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$4251 := \frac{-4^1 + 2^{14} + 5^4 - 1^0}{4^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4252 := \frac{-4^0 + 2^5 + 5^3 + 2^{12}}{-4^0 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4253 := \frac{4^7 + 2^1 + 5^4 + 3^0}{4^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4253 := \frac{4^7 + 2^1 + 5^4 + 3^0}{4^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4254 := \frac{4^0 + 2^5 + 5^3 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 2^0 - 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4255 := \frac{4^2 + 2^{14} - 5^1 + 5^4}{4^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4256 := \frac{-4^0 + 2^{12} + 5^3 + 6^2}{-4^0 + 2^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$4257 := \frac{4^3 + 2^5 + 5^3 + 7^5}{4^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4257 := \frac{4^3 + 2^5 + 5^3 + 7^5}{4^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4258 := \frac{4^0 + 2^{15} + 5^8 + 8^6}{4^3 + 2^3 + 5^2 + 8^2}$$

$$4258 := \frac{4^0 + 2^{15} + 5^8 + 8^6}{4^3 + 2^3 + 5^2 + 8^2}$$

$$4259 := \frac{4^3 + 2^9 + 5^0 + 9^5}{4^1 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 9^0}$$

$$4259 := \frac{4^3 + 2^9 + 5^0 + 9^5}{4^1 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 9^0}$$

$$4260 := \frac{4^2 + 2^{15} + 6^4 + 0^1}{4^0 + 2^0 + 6^1 + 0^1}$$

$$4261 := \frac{4^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 1^0}{4^0 - 2^1 + 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4262 := \frac{4^2 + 2^4 + 6^4 + 2^{15}}{4^0 + 2^1 + 6^0 + 2^2}$$

$$4263 := \frac{4^2 + 2^{19} + 6^2 + 3^2}{4^1 + 2^1 + 6^2 + 3^4}$$

$$4264 := \frac{4^3 + 2^{13} + 6^5 + 4^5}{4^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4265 := \frac{4^4 + 2^1 + 6^6 + 5^0}{4^0 + 2^2 + 6^0 + 5^1}$$

$$4266 := \frac{4^4 + 2^3 + 6^1 + 6^6}{4^0 + 2^3 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4267 := \frac{4^1 + 2^8 + 6^0 + 7^5}{4^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4268 := \frac{4^2 + 2^6 + 6^4 + 8^5}{4^1 + 2^1 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4269 := \frac{4^3 + 2^{19} + 6^1 + 9^3}{4^1 + 2^1 + 6^2 + 9^2}$$

$$4270 := \frac{4^2 + 2^8 + 7^5 + 0^0}{4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 0^0}$$

$$4270 := \frac{4^2 + 2^8 + 7^5 + 0^0}{4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 0^0}$$

$$4271 := \frac{4^4 + 2^{18} + 7^4 + 1^0}{4^1 + 2^3 + 7^2 + 1^0}$$

$$4271 := \frac{4^4 + 2^{18} + 7^4 + 1^0}{4^1 + 2^3 + 7^2 + 1^0}$$

$$4272 := \frac{-4^0 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 2^{12}}{-4^0 - 2^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4273 := \frac{4^4 + 2^1 + 7^5 + 3^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4273 := \frac{4^4 + 2^1 + 7^5 + 3^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4274 := \frac{4^0 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 4^4}{4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4275 := \frac{4^4 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 5^1}{4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4275 := \frac{4^4 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 5^1}{4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4276 := \frac{4^2 + 2^{13} + 7^3 + 6^0}{-4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4277 := \frac{4^5 + 2^{14} + 7^0 + 7^5}{4^1 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4277 := \frac{4^5 + 2^{14} + 7^0 + 7^5}{4^1 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4278 := \frac{-4^5 + 2^{16} - 7^3 + 8^0}{4^1 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 8^1}$$

$$4279 := \frac{4^7 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 9^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4279 := \frac{4^7 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 9^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4280 := \frac{4^2 + 2^{20} + 8^1 + 0^1}{-4^1 + 2^8 - 8^1 + 0^0}$$

$$4282 := \frac{4^7 - 2^1 + 8^5 - 2^{11}}{4^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 2^3}$$

$$4283 := \frac{4^2 + 2^4 + 8^6 + 3^{10}}{4^0 + 2^0 + 8^2 + 3^2}$$

$$4283 := \frac{4^2 + 2^4 + 8^6 + 3^{10}}{4^0 + 2^0 + 8^2 + 3^2}$$

$$4284 := \frac{-4^1 - 2^6 + 8^4 + 4^4}{-4^0 - 2^0 - 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4285 := \frac{4^4 + 2^{17} + 8^3 + 5^7}{4^1 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$4286 := \frac{4^7 + 2^5 + 8^3 + 6^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4286 := \frac{4^7 + 2^5 + 8^3 + 6^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4287 := \frac{-4^2 + 2^8 + 8^4 - 7^2}{4^0 + 2^0 - 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$4288 := \frac{4^6 + 2^{16} + 8^3 + 8^5}{4^1 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 8^1}$$

$$4289 := \frac{4^8 + 2^{13} + 8^5 + 9^3}{4^1 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$4290 := \frac{-4^4 - 2^{14} + 9^6 - 0^0}{4^0 + 2^7 - 9^1 + 0^1}$$

$$4291 := \frac{4^5 + 2^1 + 9^5 - 1^0}{4^1 + 2^3 + 9^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4292 := \frac{-4^0 + 2^8 + 9^5 - 2^{14}}{4^0 + 2^2 + 9^0 + 2^2}$$

$$4293 := \frac{4^7 + 2^5 + 9^3 + 3^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4293 := \frac{4^7 + 2^5 + 9^3 + 3^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4294 := \frac{-4^0 + 2^6 + 9^3 + 4^7}{4^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4295 := \frac{4^5 + 2^5 + 9^5 + 5^2}{4^1 + 2^2 + 9^0 + 5^1}$$

$$4295 := \frac{4^5 + 2^5 + 9^5 + 5^2}{4^1 + 2^2 + 9^0 + 5^1}$$

$$4296 := \frac{-4^0 - 2^{11} + 9^4 - 6^3}{-4^0 - 2^0 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$4297 := \frac{4^8 + 2^{18} + 9^5 + 7^0}{4^0 + 2^0 + 9^2 + 7^1}$$

$$4297 := \frac{4^8 + 2^{18} + 9^5 + 7^0}{4^0 + 2^0 + 9^2 + 7^1}$$

$$4298 := \frac{4^0 + 2^5 + 9^0 + 8^6}{-4^0 - 2^0 - 9^0 + 8^2}$$

$$4299 := \frac{4^7 + 2^1 + 9^2 + 9^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4299 := \frac{4^7 + 2^1 + 9^2 + 9^3}{4^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4302 := \frac{-4^1 + 3^8 - 0^0 + 2^{11}}{-4^0 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4303 := \frac{4^1 - 3^6 + 0^0 + 3^{11}}{4^1 + 3^2 + 0^0 + 3^3}$$

$$4304 := \frac{4^5 + 3^8 - 0^0 + 4^5}{-4^0 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4305 := \frac{-4^2 + 3^{11} - 0^0 - 5^4}{-4^1 - 3^4 + 0^0 + 5^3}$$

$$4306 := \frac{4^7 + 3^1 + 0^0 - 6^5}{-4^0 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4308 := \frac{-4^7 - 3^1 - 0^0 + 8^7}{-4^0 - 3^3 - 0^0 + 8^3}$$

$$4309 := \frac{-4^3 - 3^7 - 0^0 + 9^4}{-4^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 9^0}$$

$$4312 := \frac{4^6 + 3^6 - 1^0 - 2^9}{-4^0 - 3^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4313 := \frac{4^6 - 3^3 + 1^0 + 3^5}{4^1 - 3^0 - 1^0 - 3^0}$$

$$4314 := \frac{-4^2 + 3^{11} - 1^0 - 4^4}{-4^0 + 3^3 - 1^0 + 4^2}$$

$$4315 := \frac{4^4 + 3^9 + 1^0 - 5^6}{4^1 - 3^0 - 1^0 - 5^0}$$

$$4316 := \frac{4^6 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 6^3}{-4^0 - 3^1 - 1^0 + 6^1}$$

$$4317 := \frac{4^{11} + 3^6 + 1^0 + 7^6}{4^5 - 3^3 + 1^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4320 := \frac{4^8 - 3^6 - 2^3 + 0^0}{4^0 + 3^2 + 2^2 + 0^0}$$

$$4321 := \frac{-4^0 + 3^{11} + 2^4 - 1^0}{-4^0 + 3^2 + 2^5 + 1^0}$$

$$4322 := \frac{-4^0 + 3^5 - 2^4 + 2^{12}}{-4^0 - 3^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4323 := \frac{4^8 + 3^6 + 2^9 + 3^9}{4^0 + 3^2 + 2^0 + 3^2}$$

$$4323 := \frac{4^8 + 3^6 + 2^9 + 3^9}{4^0 + 3^2 + 2^0 + 3^2}$$

$$4324 := \frac{-4^0 - 3^3 + 2^8 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 3^0 - 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4325 := \frac{4^8 + 3^3 + 2^9 + 5^5}{4^0 + 3^2 + 2^0 + 5^1}$$

$$4325 := \frac{4^8 + 3^3 + 2^9 + 5^5}{4^0 + 3^2 + 2^0 + 5^1}$$

$$4326 := \frac{4^0 + 3^{11} + 2^1 + 6^3}{4^0 + 3^1 + 2^0 + 6^2}$$

$$4326 := \frac{4^0 + 3^{11} + 2^1 + 6^3}{4^0 + 3^1 + 2^0 + 6^2}$$

$$4327 := \frac{4^4 + 3^5 + 2^1 + 7^5}{4^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4327 := \frac{4^4 + 3^5 + 2^1 + 7^5}{4^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4328 := \frac{-4^0 + 3^{10} + 2^{14} + 8^5}{4^1 + 3^2 + 2^2 + 8^1}$$

$$4329 := \frac{4^0 + 3^0 + 2^{10} + 9^6}{4^0 + 3^2 + 2^5 + 9^2}$$

$$4329 := \frac{4^0 + 3^0 + 2^{10} + 9^6}{4^0 + 3^2 + 2^5 + 9^2}$$

$$4330 := \frac{4^6 - 3^2 + 3^5 + 0^1}{-4^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$$

$$4331 := \frac{4^6 - 3^2 + 3^5 + 1^0}{4^1 - 3^0 - 3^0 - 1^0}$$

$$4332 := \frac{4^5 + 3^2 + 3^7 + 2^{17}}{4^0 + 3^0 + 3^3 + 2^1}$$

$$4333 := \frac{4^2 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 3^{13}}{4^4 + 3^2 + 3^3 + 3^4}$$

$$4333 := \frac{4^2 + 3^7 + 3^9 + 3^{13}}{4^4 + 3^2 + 3^3 + 3^4}$$

$$4334 := \frac{-4^1 - 3^0 + 3^5 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 3^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4335 := \frac{4^6 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 5^1}{4^1 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4335 := \frac{4^6 + 3^8 + 3^9 + 5^1}{4^1 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4336 := \frac{4^{10} + 3^0 + 3^6 + 6^1}{4^2 + 3^0 + 3^2 + 6^3}$$

$$4336 := \frac{4^{10} + 3^0 + 3^6 + 6^1}{4^2 + 3^0 + 3^2 + 6^3}$$

$$4337 := \frac{4^6 - 3^0 + 3^5 - 7^0}{4^1 - 3^0 - 3^0 - 7^0}$$

$$4338 := \frac{4^9 + 3^7 + 3^8 + 8^5}{4^1 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 8^2}$$

$$4338 := \frac{4^9 + 3^7 + 3^8 + 8^5}{4^1 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 8^2}$$

$$4339 := \frac{4^7 + 3^3 + 3^{10} + 9^5}{4^1 + 3^2 + 3^2 + 9^1}$$

$$4340 := \frac{4^0 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 0^1}{-4^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$$

$$4341 := \frac{4^0 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 1^0}{-4^0 - 3^0 + 4^1 - 1^0}$$

$$4342 := \frac{4^0 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 2^1}{-4^0 - 3^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4343 := \frac{4^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 3^6}{4^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4344 := \frac{4^0 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 3^0 - 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4345 := \frac{4^2 + 3^{13} + 4^8 + 5^7}{4^2 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3}$$

$$4346 := \frac{4^0 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 6^1}{-4^0 - 3^0 + 4^1 - 6^0}$$

$$4347 := \frac{4^6 + 3^{11} + 4^9 + 7^1}{4^1 + 3^3 + 4^3 + 7^1}$$

$$4348 := \frac{4^0 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 8^1}{-4^0 - 3^0 + 4^1 - 8^0}$$

$$4349 := \frac{4^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 9^3}{4^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4350 := \frac{4^4 - 3^4 + 5^7 + 0^1}{4^1 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 0^1}$$

$$4351 := \frac{4^{10} + 3^2 + 5^1 + 1^0}{-4^1 + 3^5 + 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4352 := \frac{4^1 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 2^{11}}{4^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4353 := \frac{4^6 + 3^5 + 5^7 + 3^5}{4^1 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 3^2}$$

$$4354 := \frac{4^5 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 4^7}{4^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4355 := \frac{4^7 + 3^8 + 5^4 + 5^6}{4^1 + 3^1 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4356 := \frac{4^1 + 3^5 + 5^7 + 6^2}{4^1 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$4356 := \frac{4^1 + 3^5 + 5^7 + 6^2}{4^1 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$4357 := \frac{4^2 + 3^{10} + 5^6 + 7^5}{4^1 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4357 := \frac{4^2 + 3^{10} + 5^6 + 7^5}{4^1 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4358 := \frac{4^8 + 3^{12} + 5^1 + 8^2}{4^0 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 8^1}$$

$$4359 := \frac{4^5 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 9^5}{4^1 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 9^1}$$

$$4359 := \frac{4^5 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 9^5}{4^1 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 9^1}$$

$$4360 := \frac{4^{11} + 3^2 + 6^1 + 0^0}{4^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 0^0}$$

$$4360 := \frac{4^{11} + 3^2 + 6^1 + 0^0}{4^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 0^0}$$

$$4361 := \frac{-4^7 + 3^{10} - 6^5 - 1^0}{-4^0 + 3^2 - 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4362 := \frac{4^0 + 3^{12} + 6^6 + 2^{11}}{4^0 + 3^1 + 6^0 + 2^7}$$

$$4363 := \frac{-4^2 + 3^7 - 6^1 + 3^8}{-4^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4364 := \frac{4^5 + 3^{10} - 6^0 + 4^5}{4^0 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 4^1}$$

$$4365 := \frac{4^6 + 3^{13} + 6^5 + 5^3}{4^3 + 3^5 + 6^2 + 5^2}$$

$$4366 := \frac{4^8 - 3^2 - 6^0 - 6^2}{4^1 + 3^2 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4367 := \frac{4^2 + 3^5 + 6^0 + 7^6}{4^2 + 3^1 + 6^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4367 := \frac{4^2 + 3^5 + 6^0 + 7^6}{4^2 + 3^1 + 6^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4368 := \frac{4^8 - 3^8 + 6^0 - 8^5}{4^0 + 3^1 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4369 := \frac{4^7 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 9^5}{4^1 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$4369 := \frac{4^7 + 3^5 + 6^6 + 9^5}{4^1 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$4370 := \frac{4^9 + 3^6 + 7^5 + 0^1}{4^2 - 3^0 + 7^2 + 0^1}$$

$$4371 := \frac{4^8 + 3^3 + 7^0 + 1^0}{4^1 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 1^1}$$

$$4371 := \frac{4^8 + 3^3 + 7^0 + 1^0}{4^1 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 1^1}$$

$$4372 := \frac{4^7 + 3^6 + 7^3 + 2^5}{4^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4373 := \frac{4^8 + 3^0 + 7^2 + 3^2}{4^1 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 3^2}$$

$$4374 := \frac{4^5 + 3^4 + 7^1 + 4^7}{4^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4374 := \frac{4^5 + 3^4 + 7^1 + 4^7}{4^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4375 := \frac{4^8 + 3^4 + 7^1 + 5^0}{4^1 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 5^0}$$

$$4375 := \frac{4^8 + 3^4 + 7^1 + 5^0}{4^1 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 5^0}$$

$$4376 := \frac{4^6 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 6^2}{4^0 + 3^0 - 7^1 + 6^1}$$

$$4377 := \frac{4^7 + 3^{12} + 7^0 + 7^5}{4^1 + 3^3 + 7^2 + 7^2}$$

$$4377 := \frac{4^7 + 3^{12} + 7^0 + 7^5}{4^1 + 3^3 + 7^2 + 7^2}$$

$$4378 := \frac{4^9 + 3^6 + 7^5 + 8^3}{4^1 + 3^1 + 7^2 + 8^1}$$

$$4378 := \frac{4^9 + 3^6 + 7^5 + 8^3}{4^1 + 3^1 + 7^2 + 8^1}$$

$$4379 := \frac{4^7 + 3^0 + 7^9 + 9^1}{4^4 + 3^0 + 7^4 + 9^4}$$

$$4379 := \frac{4^7 + 3^0 + 7^9 + 9^1}{4^4 + 3^0 + 7^4 + 9^4}$$

$$4380 := \frac{4^4 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 0^0}{-4^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$4381 := \frac{4^5 + 3^{19} + 8^6 + 1^0}{4^5 + 3^7 + 8^6 + 1^0}$$

$$4381 := \frac{4^5 + 3^{19} + 8^6 + 1^0}{4^5 + 3^7 + 8^6 + 1^0}$$

$$4382 := \frac{-4^5 + 3^{12} - 8^0 + 2^{16}}{4^1 + 3^1 + 8^0 + 2^7}$$

$$4383 := \frac{4^3 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 3^9}{4^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 3^2}$$

$$4383 := \frac{4^3 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 3^9}{4^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 3^2}$$

$$4384 := \frac{-4^5 + 3^8 - 8^0 + 4^7}{-4^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4385 := \frac{4^8 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 5^6}{4^1 + 3^2 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$4385 := \frac{4^8 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 5^6}{4^1 + 3^2 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$4386 := \frac{4^7 + 3^8 + 8^6 + 6^0}{4^0 + 3^3 + 8^0 + 6^2}$$

$$4386 := \frac{4^7 + 3^8 + 8^6 + 6^0}{4^0 + 3^3 + 8^0 + 6^2}$$

$$4387 := \frac{4^1 + 3^6 + 8^1 + 7^5}{4^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4387 := \frac{4^1 + 3^6 + 8^1 + 7^5}{4^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4388 := \frac{4^8 - 3^2 + 8^0 - 8^4}{4^1 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$4389 := \frac{4^5 + 3^2 + 8^1 + 9^7}{4^5 + 3^0 + 8^2 + 9^0}$$

$$4389 := \frac{4^5 + 3^2 + 8^1 + 9^7}{4^5 + 3^0 + 8^2 + 9^0}$$

$$4390 := \frac{4^2 - 3^7 + 9^4 + 0^1}{-4^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 0^1}$$

$$4391 := \frac{4^2 - 3^7 + 9^4 + 1^0}{4^1 - 3^0 - 9^0 - 1^0}$$

$$4392 := \frac{4^2 - 3^7 + 9^4 + 2^1}{-4^0 - 3^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4393 := \frac{4^1 + 3^3 + 9^2 + 3^{12}}{4^1 + 3^2 + 9^2 + 3^3}$$

$$4393 := \frac{4^1 + 3^3 + 9^2 + 3^{12}}{4^1 + 3^2 + 9^2 + 3^3}$$

$$4394 := \frac{4^1 - 3^7 + 9^4 + 4^2}{-4^0 - 3^0 - 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4395 := \frac{4^0 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 5^3}{4^0 + 3^1 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4395 := \frac{4^0 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 5^3}{4^0 + 3^1 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4396 := \frac{4^6 + 3^{11} + 9^1 + 6^5}{4^0 + 3^3 + 9^1 + 6^1}$$

$$4397 := \frac{4^5 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 7^4}{4^1 - 3^0 - 9^0 - 7^0}$$

$$4398 := \frac{4^2 - 3^7 + 9^4 + 8^1}{4^0 + 3^0 - 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$4399 := \frac{4^{13} + 3^{10} + 9^6 + 9^7}{4^7 + 3^1 + 9^1 + 9^2}$$

$$4399 := \frac{4^{13} + 3^{10} + 9^6 + 9^7}{4^7 + 3^1 + 9^1 + 9^2}$$

$$4403 := \frac{4^3 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 3^5}{-4^0 + 4^0 + 0^1 + 3^0}$$

$$4405 := \frac{4^4 + 4^5 + 0^1 + 5^5}{-4^0 + 4^0 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$4406 := \frac{4^5 + 4^7 + 0^1 + 6^3}{4^0 + 4^0 + 0^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4406 := \frac{4^5 + 4^7 + 0^1 + 6^3}{4^0 + 4^0 + 0^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4407 := \frac{4^4 - 4^6 - 0^0 + 7^7}{-4^3 + 4^4 + 0^0 - 7^1}$$

$$4408 := \frac{4^2 + 4^{10} + 0^1 + 8^3}{-4^2 + 4^4 - 0^0 - 8^0}$$

$$4413 := \frac{4^5 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 3^5}{4^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4413 := \frac{4^5 + 4^7 + 1^0 + 3^5}{4^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4421 := \frac{-4^1 + 4^7 + 2^{18} - 1^0}{-4^0 - 4^0 + 2^6 + 1^0}$$

$$4422 := \frac{4^5 + 4^{10} + 2^1 + 2^{17}}{4^0 + 4^4 + 2^1 + 2^3}$$

$$4422 := \frac{4^5 + 4^{10} + 2^1 + 2^{17}}{4^0 + 4^4 + 2^1 + 2^3}$$

$$4423 := \frac{4^2 + 4^3 + 2^{16} + 3^6}{4^0 + 4^0 + 2^2 + 3^2}$$

$$4423 := \frac{4^2 + 4^3 + 2^{16} + 3^6}{4^0 + 4^0 + 2^2 + 3^2}$$

$$4424 := \frac{4^4 + 4^5 + 2^5 + 4^7}{4^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4425 := \frac{4^0 + 4^8 + 2^{19} + 5^5}{4^0 + 4^1 + 2^2 + 5^3}$$

$$4425 := \frac{4^0 + 4^8 + 2^{19} + 5^5}{4^0 + 4^1 + 2^2 + 5^3}$$

$$4426 := \frac{4^2 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 6^4}{4^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4426 := \frac{4^2 + 4^7 + 2^3 + 6^4}{4^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4427 := \frac{4^1 - 4^2 + 2^{12} + 7^3}{-4^0 - 4^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$4428 := \frac{-4^1 - 4^8 - 2^{15} + 8^6}{4^1 + 4^2 + 2^4 + 8^0}$$

$$4429 := \frac{-4^1 + 4^4 + 2^{12} + 9^2}{-4^0 - 4^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$4430 := \frac{-4^7 + 4^{10} - 3^0 - 0^0}{4^1 + 4^4 - 3^3 + 0^1}$$

$$4431 := \frac{4^6 + 4^{11} + 3^7 + 1^0}{4^1 + 4^5 - 3^4 + 1^0}$$

$$4432 := \frac{4^0 + 4^1 + 3^{11} + 2^7}{4^0 + 4^1 + 3^1 + 2^5}$$

$$4432 := \frac{4^0 + 4^1 + 3^{11} + 2^7}{4^0 + 4^1 + 3^1 + 2^5}$$

$$4433 := \frac{4^5 + 4^7 + 3^4 + 3^5}{4^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4433 := \frac{4^5 + 4^7 + 3^4 + 3^5}{4^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4434 := \frac{4^0 + 4^8 + 3^9 + 4^8}{4^0 + 4^2 + 3^0 + 4^2}$$

$$4435 := \frac{4^3 + 4^3 + 3^{11} + 5^3}{4^1 + 4^1 + 3^3 + 5^1}$$

$$4435 := \frac{4^3 + 4^3 + 3^{11} + 5^3}{4^1 + 4^1 + 3^3 + 5^1}$$

$$4436 := \frac{-4^0 + 4^2 + 3^8 + 6^6}{4^0 + 4^0 + 3^2 + 6^0}$$

$$4437 := \frac{4^1 + 4^3 + 3^{14} + 7^2}{4^1 + 4^5 + 3^0 + 7^2}$$

$$4437 := \frac{4^1 + 4^3 + 3^{14} + 7^2}{4^1 + 4^5 + 3^0 + 7^2}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 4438 := \frac{4^5 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 8^0}{4^0 + 4^1 + 3^2 + 8^0} & 4455 := \frac{4^6 + 4^9 + 5^5 + 5^7}{4^1 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 5^1} & 4472 := \frac{4^0 + 4^2 + 7^5 + 2^{19}}{4^1 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 2^6} \\
 4438 := \frac{4^5 + 4^8 + 3^2 + 8^0}{4^0 + 4^1 + 3^2 + 8^0} & 4456 := \frac{4^7 + 4^9 - 5^6 + 6^0}{-4^0 - 4^0 + 5^2 + 6^2} & 4473 := \frac{4^6 + 4^6 + 7^7 + 3^5}{4^3 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 3^2} \\
 4439 := \frac{4^0 + 4^3 - 3^7 + 9^4}{-4^0 + 4^1 - 3^0 - 9^0} & 4457 := \frac{-4^1 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 7^5}{4^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 7^0} & 4473 := \frac{4^6 + 4^6 + 7^7 + 3^5}{4^3 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 3^2} \\
 4442 := \frac{4^1 + 4^5 + 4^8 + 2^{18}}{4^0 + 4^0 + 4^3 + 2^3} & 4459 := \frac{-4^0 + 4^5 - 5^5 + 9^4}{-4^0 + 4^1 - 5^0 - 9^0} & 4474 := \frac{4^0 + 4^3 + 7^5 + 4^5}{4^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 4^0} \\
 4442 := \frac{4^1 + 4^5 + 4^8 + 2^{18}}{4^0 + 4^0 + 4^3 + 2^3} & 4462 := \frac{4^5 + 4^6 + 6^7 + 2^9}{4^1 + 4^2 + 6^2 + 2^3} & 4474 := \frac{4^0 + 4^3 + 7^5 + 4^5}{4^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 4^0} \\
 4443 := \frac{4^1 + 4^5 + 4^8 + 3^4}{4^1 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 3^1} & 4462 := \frac{4^5 + 4^6 + 6^7 + 2^9}{4^1 + 4^2 + 6^2 + 2^3} & 4475 := \frac{4^3 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 5^1}{4^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 5^0} \\
 4445 := \frac{-4^4 - 4^7 + 4^8 - 5^0}{4^0 + 4^0 + 4^1 + 5^1} & 4463 := \frac{4^1 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 3^{15}}{4^1 + 4^5 + 6^0 + 3^7} & 4475 := \frac{4^3 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 5^1}{4^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 5^0} \\
 4446 := \frac{4^5 + 4^6 + 4^{10} + 6^1}{4^0 + 4^1 + 4^2 + 6^3} & 4463 := \frac{4^1 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 3^{15}}{4^1 + 4^5 + 6^0 + 3^7} & 4476 := \frac{4^0 + 4^6 + 7^3 + 6^2}{4^0 + 4^0 - 7^1 + 6^1} \\
 4446 := \frac{4^5 + 4^6 + 4^{10} + 6^1}{4^0 + 4^1 + 4^2 + 6^3} & 4464 := \frac{4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7}{4^0 + 4^1 + 6^0 + 4^1} & 4477 := \frac{4^2 + 4^9 - 7^6 - 7^6}{-4^0 - 4^0 + 7^0 + 7^1} \\
 4447 := \frac{4^1 + 4^1 + 4^6 + 7^3}{-4^0 - 4^0 + 4^1 - 7^0} & 4464 := \frac{4^6 + 4^7 + 6^5 + 4^7}{4^0 + 4^1 + 6^0 + 4^1} & 4478 := \frac{-4^0 + 4^{10} + 7^5 - 8^4}{4^1 + 4^3 - 7^3 + 8^3} \\
 4448 := \frac{4^3 + 4^7 + 4^9 + 8^5}{4^0 + 4^0 + 4^1 + 8^2} & 4465 := \frac{-4^7 + 4^8 - 6^2 - 5^0}{4^0 + 4^1 + 6^0 + 5^1} & 4479 := \frac{4^1 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 9^2}{4^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 9^0} \\
 4448 := \frac{4^3 + 4^7 + 4^9 + 8^5}{4^0 + 4^0 + 4^1 + 8^2} & 4466 := \frac{4^1 - 4^8 - 6^2 + 6^7}{-4^1 + 4^3 - 6^1 - 6^1} & 4479 := \frac{4^1 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 9^2}{4^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 9^0} \\
 4449 := \frac{4^2 + 4^9 + 4^{12} + 9^7}{4^2 + 4^3 + 4^6 + 9^3} & 4467 := \frac{4^0 + 4^5 + 6^2 + 7^5}{4^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 7^0} & 4480 := \frac{4^5 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 0^1}{4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 0^0} \\
 4452 := \frac{4^0 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 2^{11}}{4^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 2^0} & 4467 := \frac{4^0 + 4^5 + 6^2 + 7^5}{4^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 7^0} & 4480 := \frac{4^5 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 0^1}{4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 0^0} \\
 4453 := \frac{4^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 3^{10}}{4^1 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 3^2} & 4468 := \frac{4^6 + 4^9 + 6^5 + 8^6}{4^1 + 4^2 + 6^2 + 8^2} & 4482 := \frac{4^5 + 4^7 + 8^1 + 2^9}{4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 2^0} \\
 4453 := \frac{4^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 3^{10}}{4^1 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 3^2} & 4468 := \frac{4^6 + 4^9 + 6^5 + 8^6}{4^1 + 4^2 + 6^2 + 8^2} & 4482 := \frac{4^5 + 4^7 + 8^1 + 2^9}{4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 2^0} \\
 4454 := \frac{-4^0 + 4^5 + 5^7 + 4^5}{-4^0 + 4^1 - 5^0 + 4^2} & 4469 := \frac{4^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^2}{-4^0 - 4^0 - 6^1 + 9^1} & 4483 := \frac{4^1 + 4^6 + 8^4 + 3^{10}}{4^0 + 4^1 + 8^0 + 3^2} \\
 4455 := \frac{4^6 + 4^9 + 5^5 + 5^7}{4^1 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 5^1} & 4470 := \frac{-4^2 + 4^{11} - 7^6 + 0^0}{-4^3 + 4^5 - 7^2 + 0^0} & 4483 := \frac{4^1 + 4^6 + 8^4 + 3^{10}}{4^0 + 4^1 + 8^0 + 3^2}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 4484 := \frac{4^2 + 4^5 + 8^3 + 4^7}{4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 4^0} & 4498 := \frac{4^0 - 4^3 + 9^5 - 8^3}{-4^0 + 4^1 + 9^1 + 8^0} & 4516 := \frac{4^9 - 5^0 + 1^0 - 6^3}{4^2 + 5^1 + 1^0 + 6^2} \\
 4484 := \frac{4^2 + 4^5 + 8^3 + 4^7}{4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 4^0} & 4499 := \frac{4^4 + 4^9 - 9^3 - 9^3}{-4^1 + 4^3 - 9^0 - 9^0} & 4520 := \frac{-4^2 + 5^6 - 2^{11} - 0^0}{4^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 0^1} \\
 4485 := \frac{4^4 + 4^6 + 8^1 + 5^3}{-4^0 - 4^0 + 8^1 - 5^1} & 4502 := \frac{4^7 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 2^5}{4^1 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 2^4} & 4521 := \frac{-4^9 + 5^9 - 2^7 + 1^0}{4^1 + 5^4 - 2^8 + 1^0} \\
 4486 := \frac{4^4 + 4^7 + 8^1 + 6^4}{4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 6^0} & 4502 := \frac{4^7 + 5^7 + 0^0 + 2^5}{4^1 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 2^4} & 4522 := \frac{4^0 + 5^0 + 2^6 + 2^{17}}{4^0 + 5^2 + 2^0 + 2^1} \\
 4486 := \frac{4^4 + 4^7 + 8^1 + 6^4}{4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 6^0} & 4503 := \frac{-4^6 + 5^8 + 0^1 + 3^6}{4^1 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 3^4} & 4522 := \frac{4^0 + 5^0 + 2^6 + 2^{17}}{4^0 + 5^2 + 2^0 + 2^1} \\
 4487 := \frac{4^2 + 4^{10} + 8^5 + 7^1}{4^3 + 4^3 + 8^2 + 7^2} & 4504 := \frac{4^6 + 5^8 - 0^0 - 4^7}{-4^1 + 5^2 - 0^0 + 4^3} & 4523 := \frac{4^3 + 5^3 + 2^{18} + 3^0}{4^1 + 5^2 + 2^1 + 3^3} \\
 4487 := \frac{4^2 + 4^{10} + 8^5 + 7^1}{4^3 + 4^3 + 8^2 + 7^2} & 4505 := \frac{-4^3 + 5^6 - 0^0 + 5^9}{-4^3 - 5^3 + 0^0 + 5^4} & 4523 := \frac{4^3 + 5^3 + 2^{18} + 3^0}{4^1 + 5^2 + 2^1 + 3^3} \\
 4488 := \frac{4^3 - 4^5 + 8^4 + 8^5}{-4^0 + 4^2 + 8^0 - 8^1} & 4506 := \frac{4^{10} + 5^2 + 0^0 + 6^4}{4^2 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 6^3} & 4524 := \frac{-4^0 + 5^6 - 2^{11} - 4^1}{-4^0 - 5^0 + 2^0 + 4^1} \\
 4489 := \frac{4^2 + 4^8 + 8^6 + 9^0}{4^1 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^0} & 4506 := \frac{4^{10} + 5^2 + 0^0 + 6^4}{4^2 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 6^3} & 4525 := \frac{4^4 + 5^2 + 2^{18} + 5^2}{4^1 + 5^2 + 2^2 + 5^2} \\
 4489 := \frac{4^2 + 4^8 + 8^6 + 9^0}{4^1 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^0} & 4507 := \frac{4^0 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 7^4}{4^0 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 7^0} & 4525 := \frac{4^4 + 5^2 + 2^{18} + 5^2}{4^1 + 5^2 + 2^2 + 5^2} \\
 4490 := \frac{-4^4 + 4^8 + 9^4 - 0^0}{-4^0 + 4^2 + 9^0 + 0^1} & 4507 := \frac{4^0 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 7^4}{4^0 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 7^0} & 4526 := \frac{4^0 + 5^5 + 2^2 + 6^6}{4^0 + 5^0 + 2^3 + 6^0} \\
 4492 := \frac{-4^0 + 4^3 + 9^3 + 2^{13}}{-4^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 2^0} & 4508 := \frac{-4^8 + 5^8 - 0^0 - 8^3}{4^1 + 5^1 - 0^0 + 8^2} & 4526 := \frac{4^0 + 5^5 + 2^2 + 6^6}{4^0 + 5^0 + 2^3 + 6^0} \\
 4493 := \frac{-4^4 - 4^5 + 9^5 + 3^{10}}{4^1 + 4^1 + 9^1 + 3^2} & 4509 := \frac{4^8 + 5^6 + 0^1 + 9^0}{4^1 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 9^1} & 4527 := \frac{4^8 + 5^1 + 2^{13} + 7^5}{4^1 + 5^0 + 2^3 + 7^1} \\
 4494 := \frac{-4^0 - 4^5 + 9^5 - 4^6}{4^0 + 4^0 + 9^1 + 4^0} & 4509 := \frac{4^8 + 5^6 + 0^1 + 9^0}{4^1 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 9^1} & 4527 := \frac{4^8 + 5^1 + 2^{13} + 7^5}{4^1 + 5^0 + 2^3 + 7^1} \\
 4495 := \frac{-4^7 + 4^{11} - 9^4 + 5^0}{-4^2 + 4^5 - 9^2 + 5^0} & 4512 := \frac{-4^8 + 5^8 - 1^0 - 2^{17}}{4^0 + 5^2 + 1^0 + 2^4} & 4528 := \frac{-4^0 + 5^6 - 2^{11} + 8^1}{-4^0 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 8^0} \\
 4496 := \frac{4^0 + 4^9 - 9^2 - 6^4}{-4^0 - 4^2 + 9^2 - 6^1} & 4513 := \frac{-4^4 - 5^3 + 1^0 + 3^{10}}{4^1 + 5^1 + 1^1 + 3^1} & 4529 := \frac{4^4 + 5^1 + 2^{12} + 9^5}{4^1 + 5^0 + 2^3 + 9^0} \\
 4497 := \frac{4^6 + 4^6 + 9^6 + 7^1}{4^2 + 4^2 + 9^2 + 7^1} & 4514 := \frac{-4^4 - 5^6 - 1^0 + 4^8}{4^0 + 5^1 + 1^0 + 4^1} & 4529 := \frac{4^4 + 5^1 + 2^{12} + 9^5}{4^1 + 5^0 + 2^3 + 9^0} \\
 4497 := \frac{4^6 + 4^6 + 9^6 + 7^1}{4^2 + 4^2 + 9^2 + 7^1} & 4515 := \frac{-4^4 - 5^6 + 1^0 + 5^8}{-4^2 - 5^2 - 1^0 + 5^3} & 4530 := \frac{-4^1 + 5^6 - 3^8 + 0^1}{-4^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 0^0}
 \end{array}$$

$$4531 := \frac{-4^0 + 5^6 - 3^8 - 1^0}{-4^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4532 := \frac{4^3 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 2^{14}}{4^0 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4532 := \frac{4^3 + 5^3 + 3^9 + 2^{14}}{4^0 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4533 := \frac{4^{11} + 5^5 + 3^2 + 3^{10}}{4^1 + 5^3 + 3^4 + 3^6}$$

$$4533 := \frac{4^{11} + 5^5 + 3^2 + 3^{10}}{4^1 + 5^3 + 3^4 + 3^6}$$

$$4534 := \frac{4^3 + 5^5 + 3^{11} + 4^5}{4^1 + 5^1 + 3^3 + 4^1}$$

$$4534 := \frac{4^3 + 5^5 + 3^{11} + 4^5}{4^1 + 5^1 + 3^3 + 4^1}$$

$$4535 := \frac{4^0 + 5^1 - 3^8 + 5^6}{-4^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4536 := \frac{4^7 + 5^1 + 3^9 + 6^3}{4^0 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4536 := \frac{4^7 + 5^1 + 3^9 + 6^3}{4^0 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4537 := \frac{4^6 + 5^2 + 3^6 + 7^6}{4^2 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 7^1}$$

$$4537 := \frac{4^6 + 5^2 + 3^6 + 7^6}{4^2 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 7^1}$$

$$4538 := \frac{4^5 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 8^3}{4^0 + 5^0 + 3^2 + 8^1}$$

$$4538 := \frac{4^5 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 8^3}{4^0 + 5^0 + 3^2 + 8^1}$$

$$4539 := \frac{4^7 + 5^7 + 3^4 + 9^3}{4^1 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$4539 := \frac{4^7 + 5^7 + 3^4 + 9^3}{4^1 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$4542 := \frac{4^0 - 5^6 + 4^5 + 2^{15}}{4^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4543 := \frac{4^0 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 3^{10}}{4^0 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 3^1}$$

$$4543 := \frac{4^0 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 3^{10}}{4^0 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 3^1}$$

$$4545 := \frac{4^5 + 5^5 + 4^{12} + 5^9}{4^2 + 5^1 + 4^6 + 5^1}$$

$$4545 := \frac{4^5 + 5^5 + 4^{12} + 5^9}{4^2 + 5^1 + 4^6 + 5^1}$$

$$4546 := \frac{-4^0 + 5^2 + 4^8 + 6^7}{4^0 + 5^1 + 4^3 + 6^1}$$

$$4547 := \frac{4^6 + 5^6 + 4^9 + 7^2}{4^1 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 7^2}$$

$$4547 := \frac{4^6 + 5^6 + 4^9 + 7^2}{4^1 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 7^2}$$

$$4548 := \frac{-4^0 + 5^7 + 4^6 + 8^8}{-4^4 - 5^3 + 4^6 - 8^1}$$

$$4549 := \frac{4^4 + 5^6 + 4^{10} + 9^1}{4^3 + 5^2 + 4^3 + 9^2}$$

$$4549 := \frac{4^4 + 5^6 + 4^{10} + 9^1}{4^3 + 5^2 + 4^3 + 9^2}$$

$$4551 := \frac{-4^7 + 5^6 + 5^7 + 1^0}{-4^1 - 5^1 + 5^2 + 1^0}$$

$$4552 := \frac{4^1 - 5^4 + 5^5 + 2^{11}}{-4^0 - 5^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4553 := \frac{4^4 + 5^7 + 5^{10} + 3^{11}}{4^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 3^7}$$

$$4553 := \frac{4^4 + 5^7 + 5^{10} + 3^{11}}{4^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 3^7}$$

$$4554 := \frac{-4^4 + 5^3 + 5^6 + 4^7}{4^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4555 := \frac{4^7 + 5^0 - 5^3 + 5^6}{4^1 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4556 := \frac{4^7 + 5^4 - 5^5 - 6^3}{-4^0 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 6^1}$$

$$4557 := \frac{-4^2 + 5^1 - 5^5 + 7^5}{4^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4558 := \frac{4^6 - 5^2 - 5^2 + 8^3}{-4^0 - 5^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$4559 := \frac{-4^2 + 5^4 + 5^6 + 9^4}{4^1 - 5^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4561 := \frac{-4^{10} + 5^8 + 6^8 - 1^0}{4^1 + 5^1 + 6^3 - 1^0}$$

$$4562 := \frac{4^9 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 2^9}{4^1 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 2^4}$$

$$4562 := \frac{4^9 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 2^9}{4^1 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 2^4}$$

$$4563 := \frac{-4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 3^6}{-4^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4564 := \frac{4^0 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 4^8}{4^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4565 := \frac{4^9 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 5^8}{4^2 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 5^3}$$

$$4565 := \frac{4^9 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 5^8}{4^2 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 5^3}$$

$$4566 := \frac{4^0 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 6^{10}}{4^6 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 6^5}$$

$$4567 := \frac{4^9 + 5^3 + 6^3 + 7^4}{4^2 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$4567 := \frac{4^9 + 5^3 + 6^3 + 7^4}{4^2 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$4568 := \frac{4^1 + 5^7 - 6^0 + 8^4}{4^1 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 8^1}$$

$$4569 := \frac{4^9 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 9^6}{4^1 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 9^1}$$

$$4569 := \frac{4^9 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 9^6}{4^1 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 9^1}$$

$$4572 := \frac{4^7 + 5^5 + 7^6 + 2^1}{4^2 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 2^3}$$

$$4573 := \frac{4^7 + 5^6 + 7^0 + 3^0}{4^1 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4574 := \frac{4^3 + 5^6 + 7^5 + 4^6}{4^0 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4575 := \frac{4^5 + 5^3 + 7^8 + 5^5}{4^1 + 5^4 + 7^1 + 5^4}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 4575 := \frac{4^5 + 5^3 + 7^8 + 5^5}{4^1 + 5^4 + 7^1 + 5^4} & 4587 := \frac{4^5 + 5^1 + 8^3 + 7^5}{4^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 7^0} & 4603 := \frac{4^6 + 6^4 + 0^0 + 3^{10}}{4^1 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 3^2} \\
 4576 := \frac{4^{10} + 5^2 + 7^5 + 6^7}{4^1 + 5^2 + 7^2 + 6^3} & 4588 := \frac{-4^0 + 5^7 - 8^2 - 8^2}{-4^0 + 5^2 + 8^0 - 8^1} & 4605 := \frac{4^9 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 5^3}{4^2 + 6^2 + 0^1 + 5^1} \\
 4576 := \frac{4^{10} + 5^2 + 7^5 + 6^7}{4^1 + 5^2 + 7^2 + 6^3} & 4589 := \frac{4^1 + 5^4 + 8^7 + 9^5}{4^4 + 5^3 + 8^1 + 9^2} & 4605 := \frac{4^9 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 5^3}{4^2 + 6^2 + 0^1 + 5^1} \\
 4577 := \frac{4^8 + 5^5 + 7^0 - 7^1}{4^1 + 5^1 - 7^0 + 7^1} & 4589 := \frac{4^1 + 5^4 + 8^7 + 9^5}{4^4 + 5^3 + 8^1 + 9^2} & 4606 := \frac{4^5 + 6^1 + 0^1 + 6^7}{4^3 - 6^0 - 0^0 - 6^0} \\
 4578 := \frac{4^8 + 5^5 + 7^0 + 8^1}{4^0 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 8^1} & 4590 := \frac{4^7 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 0^1}{-4^0 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 0^1} & 4608 := \frac{4^6 - 6^0 + 0^0 + 8^3}{-4^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 8^0} \\
 4578 := \frac{4^8 + 5^5 + 7^0 + 8^1}{4^0 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 8^1} & 4591 := \frac{4^1 + 5^7 - 9^2 - 1^0}{4^1 + 5^1 + 9^1 - 1^0} & 4609 := \frac{4^6 - 6^3 + 0^1 + 9^3}{-4^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 9^0} \\
 4579 := \frac{4^{10} + 5^1 + 7^0 + 9^1}{4^2 + 5^3 + 7^1 + 9^2} & 4592 := \frac{4^6 - 5^2 + 9^1 + 2^9}{-4^0 - 5^0 + 9^0 + 2^1} & 4613 := \frac{4^3 - 6^4 + 1^0 + 3^9}{4^0 + 6^0 + 1^0 + 3^0} \\
 4579 := \frac{4^{10} + 5^1 + 7^0 + 9^1}{4^2 + 5^3 + 7^1 + 9^2} & 4593 := \frac{4^6 + 5^5 + 9^4 - 3^1}{4^1 - 5^0 - 9^0 + 3^0} & 4614 := \frac{4^0 + 6^6 + 1^0 + 4^6}{-4^2 - 6^2 - 1^0 + 4^3} \\
 4580 := \frac{-4^4 + 5^7 - 8^1 - 0^0}{4^1 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 0^1} & 4594 := \frac{4^6 + 5^7 + 9^5 + 4^{10}}{4^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 4^4} & 4619 := \frac{-4^4 - 6^0 + 1^0 + 9^6}{-4^0 + 6^2 - 1^0 + 9^2} \\
 4581 := \frac{4^7 - 5^5 - 8^4 - 1^0}{-4^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 1^0} & 4594 := \frac{4^6 + 5^7 + 9^5 + 4^{10}}{4^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 4^4} & 4620 := \frac{4^{10} + 6^7 + 2^{11} + 0^1}{4^3 + 6^3 + 2^3 + 0^3} \\
 4582 := \frac{4^0 + 5^6 + 8^2 + 2^{14}}{4^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 2^2} & 4595 := \frac{4^6 - 5^3 - 9^0 + 5^4}{4^1 - 5^0 - 9^0 - 5^0} & 4620 := \frac{4^{10} + 6^7 + 2^{11} + 0^1}{4^3 + 6^3 + 2^3 + 0^3} \\
 4582 := \frac{4^0 + 5^6 + 8^2 + 2^{14}}{4^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 2^2} & 4596 := \frac{-4^3 - 5^5 + 9^1 + 6^5}{-4^0 - 5^0 + 9^1 - 6^1} & 4622 := \frac{4^7 + 6^5 + 2^1 + 2^{13}}{4^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 2^2} \\
 4583 := \frac{4^{14} + 5^{10} + 8^5 + 3^4}{4^5 + 5^3 + 8^3 + 3^{10}} & 4597 := \frac{4^2 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 7^1}{4^1 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 7^1} & 4623 := \frac{4^7 + 6^5 + 2^{13} + 3^2}{4^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 3^1} \\
 4583 := \frac{4^{14} + 5^{10} + 8^5 + 3^4}{4^5 + 5^3 + 8^3 + 3^{10}} & 4597 := \frac{4^2 + 5^7 + 9^0 + 7^1}{4^1 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 7^1} & 4624 := \frac{4^2 + 6^5 + 2^{13} + 4^7}{4^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 4^1} \\
 4584 := \frac{4^0 - 5^2 + 8^3 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 5^0 - 8^0 + 4^1} & 4598 := \frac{4^6 - 5^0 - 9^1 + 8^3}{4^0 + 5^0 - 9^1 + 8^1} & 4624 := \frac{4^2 + 6^5 + 2^{13} + 4^7}{4^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 4^1} \\
 4585 := \frac{4^9 - 5^0 - 8^5 - 5^3}{4^2 + 5^0 + 8^1 + 5^2} & 4599 := \frac{4^2 + 5^5 + 9^3 + 9^3}{4^1 - 5^0 - 9^0 - 9^0} & 4625 := \frac{4^2 + 6^7 + 2^{11} + 5^3}{4^1 + 6^2 + 2^4 + 5^1} \\
 4586 := \frac{-4^0 - 5^5 - 8^2 + 6^5}{-4^0 - 5^1 + 8^0 + 6^1} & 4602 := \frac{4^6 - 6^1 + 0^1 + 2^9}{-4^0 - 6^0 + 0^0 + 2^1} & 4625 := \frac{4^2 + 6^7 + 2^{11} + 5^3}{4^1 + 6^2 + 2^4 + 5^1} \\
 4587 := \frac{4^5 + 5^1 + 8^3 + 7^5}{4^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 7^0} & 4603 := \frac{4^6 + 6^4 + 0^0 + 3^{10}}{4^1 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 3^2} & 4626 := \frac{4^7 + 6^2 + 2^{11} + 6^2}{4^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}
 \end{array}$$

$$4626 := \frac{4^7 + 6^2 + 2^{11} + 6^2}{4^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4627 := \frac{4^4 + 6^7 + 2^{11} + 7^1}{4^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 7^2}$$

$$4627 := \frac{4^4 + 6^7 + 2^{11} + 7^1}{4^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 7^2}$$

$$4628 := \frac{4^7 + 6^3 + 2^{13} + 8^6}{4^2 + 6^1 + 2^5 + 8^1}$$

$$4628 := \frac{4^7 + 6^3 + 2^{13} + 8^6}{4^2 + 6^1 + 2^5 + 8^1}$$

$$4629 := \frac{4^6 + 6^4 + 2^{15} + 9^5}{4^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 9^1}$$

$$4629 := \frac{4^6 + 6^4 + 2^{15} + 9^5}{4^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 9^1}$$

$$4630 := \frac{-4^9 + 6^7 + 3^6 - 0^0}{4^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 0^0}$$

$$4631 := \frac{4^8 - 6^5 - 3^7 - 1^0}{4^0 + 6^0 + 3^2 + 1^0}$$

$$4632 := \frac{-4^0 + 6^6 + 3^2 - 2^{15}}{-4^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4633 := \frac{4^7 + 6^6 + 3^6 + 3^{11}}{4^1 + 6^2 + 3^1 + 3^2}$$

$$4633 := \frac{4^7 + 6^6 + 3^6 + 3^{11}}{4^1 + 6^2 + 3^1 + 3^2}$$

$$4634 := \frac{4^0 - 6^2 + 3^7 + 4^7}{4^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4635 := \frac{4^{12} + 6^3 + 3^9 + 5^3}{4^2 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 5^3}$$

$$4635 := \frac{4^{12} + 6^3 + 3^9 + 5^3}{4^2 + 6^4 + 3^7 + 5^3}$$

$$4636 := \frac{4^6 + 6^0 + 3^5 + 6^6}{4^0 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 6^1}$$

$$4636 := \frac{4^6 + 6^0 + 3^5 + 6^6}{4^0 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 6^1}$$

$$4637 := \frac{4^7 + 6^1 - 3^5 + 7^4}{4^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4638 := \frac{4^7 + 6^0 + 3^{12} + 8^4}{4^0 + 6^2 + 3^4 + 8^0}$$

$$4638 := \frac{4^7 + 6^0 + 3^{12} + 8^4}{4^0 + 6^2 + 3^4 + 8^0}$$

$$4639 := \frac{4^4 + 6^7 + 3^{11} + 9^4}{4^1 + 6^1 + 3^2 + 9^2}$$

$$4639 := \frac{4^4 + 6^7 + 3^{11} + 9^4}{4^1 + 6^1 + 3^2 + 9^2}$$

$$4640 := \frac{-4^0 + 6^6 - 4^4 + 0^0}{4^1 + 6^0 + 4^1 + 0^0}$$

$$4641 := \frac{-4^0 - 6^0 + 4^{12} + 1^0}{-4^3 + 6^5 - 4^6 - 1^0}$$

$$4642 := \frac{4^4 + 6^7 + 4^7 + 2^9}{4^1 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 2^3}$$

$$4642 := \frac{4^4 + 6^7 + 4^7 + 2^9}{4^1 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 2^3}$$

$$4643 := \frac{4^0 + 6^6 + 4^2 - 3^5}{4^1 + 6^0 + 4^1 + 3^0}$$

$$4644 := \frac{4^4 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 6^0 - 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4645 := \frac{-4^2 + 6^{10} + 4^7 + 5^0}{4^5 + 6^5 + 4^6 + 5^3}$$

$$4646 := \frac{4^7 + 6^2 + 4^9 + 6^6}{4^1 + 6^0 + 4^3 + 6^0}$$

$$4646 := \frac{4^7 + 6^2 + 4^9 + 6^6}{4^1 + 6^0 + 4^3 + 6^0}$$

$$4647 := \frac{-4^0 + 6^0 - 4^5 + 7^7}{-4^2 + 6^3 - 4^2 - 7^1}$$

$$4648 := \frac{4^3 + 6^4 + 4^{10} + 8^3}{4^0 + 6^3 + 4^0 + 8^1}$$

$$4649 := \frac{4^4 + 6^3 + 4^6 + 9^2}{-4^0 - 6^0 + 4^1 - 9^0}$$

$$4650 := \frac{-4^0 + 6^5 - 5^5 + 0^1}{-4^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$4651 := \frac{-4^0 + 6^5 - 5^5 + 1^0}{4^0 - 6^1 + 5^1 + 1^0}$$

$$4652 := \frac{-4^0 + 6^5 - 5^5 + 2^1}{-4^0 - 6^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4653 := \frac{4^7 + 6^2 + 5^1 + 3^7}{4^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4653 := \frac{4^7 + 6^2 + 5^1 + 3^7}{4^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4654 := \frac{-4^0 + 6^5 - 5^5 + 4^1}{-4^0 - 6^0 - 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4655 := \frac{-4^0 + 6^5 + 5^1 - 5^5}{4^0 - 6^1 + 5^0 + 5^1}$$

$$4656 := \frac{-4^0 + 6^1 - 5^5 + 6^5}{-4^0 + 6^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$4657 := \frac{4^1 + 6^3 + 5^8 + 7^3}{4^1 + 6^1 + 5^2 + 7^2}$$

$$4657 := \frac{4^1 + 6^3 + 5^8 + 7^3}{4^1 + 6^1 + 5^2 + 7^2}$$

$$4658 := \frac{-4^0 + 6^5 - 5^5 + 8^1}{-4^0 - 6^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$4659 := \frac{4^0 + 6^0 + 5^8 + 9^3}{4^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 9^2}$$

$$4659 := \frac{4^0 + 6^0 + 5^8 + 9^3}{4^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 9^2}$$

$$4662 := \frac{4^6 + 6^3 + 6^3 + 2^{15}}{4^1 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4662 := \frac{4^6 + 6^3 + 6^3 + 2^{15}}{4^1 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4663 := \frac{4^5 + 6^4 + 6^7 + 3^7}{4^2 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 3^1}$$

$$4663 := \frac{4^5 + 6^4 + 6^7 + 3^7}{4^2 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 3^1}$$

$$4664 := \frac{4^7 + 6^4 + 6^6 + 4^9}{4^1 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 4^3}$$

$$4664 := \frac{4^7 + 6^4 + 6^6 + 4^9}{4^1 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 4^3}$$

$$4665 := \frac{-4^0 - 6^1 + 6^6 + 5^0}{-4^0 + 6^1 + 6^1 - 5^0}$$

$$4666 := \frac{-4^4 - 6^4 - 6^5 + 6^6}{4^1 - 6^0 - 6^0 + 6^1}$$

$$4667 := \frac{4^0 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 7^1}{4^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4667 := \frac{4^0 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 7^1}{4^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4668 := \frac{4^2 + 6^2 + 6^7 + 8^5}{4^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 8^2}$$

$$4668 := \frac{4^2 + 6^2 + 6^7 + 8^5}{4^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 8^2}$$

$$4669 := \frac{4^6 + 6^1 + 6^4 - 9^3}{-4^0 - 6^0 - 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$4670 := \frac{4^4 + 6^7 + 7^1 + 0^0}{4^1 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 0^0}$$

$$4670 := \frac{4^4 + 6^7 + 7^1 + 0^0}{4^1 + 6^1 + 7^2 + 0^0}$$

$$4671 := \frac{4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0}{4^0 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 1^0}$$

$$4671 := \frac{4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 1^0}{4^0 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 1^0}$$

$$4672 := \frac{4^7 + 6^0 - 7^4 + 2^5}{-4^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4673 := \frac{4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^2}{4^0 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 3^0}$$

$$4673 := \frac{4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 3^2}{4^0 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 3^0}$$

$$4674 := \frac{4^0 + 6^9 + 7^8 + 4^7}{4^5 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 4^5}$$

$$4674 := \frac{4^0 + 6^9 + 7^8 + 4^7}{4^5 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 4^5}$$

$$4675 := \frac{4^8 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 5^0}{4^2 + 6^1 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4675 := \frac{4^8 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 5^0}{4^2 + 6^1 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4677 := \frac{4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2}{4^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4677 := \frac{4^2 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 7^2}{4^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4678 := \frac{-4^2 + 6^0 - 7^1 + 8^5}{4^1 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4679 := \frac{4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2}{4^0 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 9^0}$$

$$4679 := \frac{4^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^2}{4^0 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 9^0}$$

$$4680 := \frac{-4^0 - 6^1 + 8^5 - 0^0}{4^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 0^0}$$

$$4681 := \frac{-4^0 - 6^0 + 8^5 + 1^0}{4^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4682 := \frac{4^0 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 2^2}{4^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 2^2}$$

$$4682 := \frac{4^0 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 2^2}{4^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 2^2}$$

$$4683 := \frac{4^1 + 6^1 + 8^5 + 3^1}{4^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4683 := \frac{4^1 + 6^1 + 8^5 + 3^1}{4^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4684 := \frac{4^7 + 6^7 + 8^4 + 4^{10}}{4^1 + 6^3 + 8^2 + 4^1}$$

$$4684 := \frac{4^7 + 6^7 + 8^4 + 4^{10}}{4^1 + 6^3 + 8^2 + 4^1}$$

$$4685 := \frac{4^0 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 5^2}{4^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4686 := \frac{-4^0 - 6^0 + 8^5 + 6^2}{4^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4687 := \frac{4^1 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 7^0}{4^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4687 := \frac{4^1 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 7^0}{4^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4688 := \frac{4^1 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 8^5}{4^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4688 := \frac{4^1 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 8^5}{4^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4689 := \frac{-4^3 - 6^4 - 8^3 + 9^4}{-4^0 + 6^0 - 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$4691 := \frac{4^4 + 6^6 - 9^0 - 1^0}{-4^0 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 1^0}$$

$$4692 := \frac{4^0 - 6^1 + 9^2 + 2^{15}}{4^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 2^2}$$

$$4693 := \frac{4^3 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 3^{11}}{4^1 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 3^1}$$

$$4693 := \frac{4^3 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 3^{11}}{4^1 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 3^1}$$

$$4694 := \frac{4^0 + 6^5 + 9^4 - 4^4}{-4^0 - 6^0 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4695 := \frac{4^5 + 6^6 - 9^3 - 5^0}{-4^0 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$4696 := \frac{4^8 + 6^0 - 9^1 + 6^3}{4^0 + 6^1 + 9^0 + 6^1}$$

$$4697 := \frac{4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2}{4^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4697 := \frac{4^4 + 6^6 + 9^1 + 7^2}{4^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4698 := \frac{4^0 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 8^5}{4^1 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4698 := \frac{4^0 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 8^5}{4^1 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4699 := \frac{4^{11} - 6^3 + 9^2 - 9^5}{4^3 + 6^1 + 9^2 + 9^3}$$

$$4702 := \frac{-4^{11} + 7^8 + 0^0 - 2^{20}}{-4^0 + 7^2 - 0^0 + 2^6}$$

$$4703 := \frac{4^7 + 7^4 + 0^1 + 3^3}{4^0 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4703 := \frac{4^7 + 7^4 + 0^1 + 3^3}{4^0 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4704 := \frac{4^2 + 7^6 - 0^0 - 4^3}{4^0 + 7^1 + 0^0 + 4^2}$$

$$4705 := \frac{4^0 + 7^6 + 0^1 - 5^2}{4^2 + 7^1 + 0^0 + 5^0}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 4706 := \frac{4^8 + 7^3 - 0^0 + 6^1}{4^0 + 7^1 + 0^1 + 6^1} & 4723 := \frac{4^0 + 7^2 + 2^{15} + 3^5}{4^0 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 3^1} & 4734 := \frac{4^5 + 7^5 + 3^4 + 4^5}{4^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 4^0} \\
 4708 := \frac{-4^4 + 7^7 + 0^0 - 8^4}{4^1 - 7^3 + 0^0 + 8^3} & 4723 := \frac{4^0 + 7^2 + 2^{15} + 3^5}{4^0 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 3^1} & 4735 := \frac{4^5 + 7^3 + 3^{13} + 5^1}{4^4 + 7^2 + 3^3 + 5^1} \\
 4709 := \frac{-4^1 + 7^6 - 0^0 + 9^2}{4^2 + 7^1 + 0^0 + 9^0} & 4724 := \frac{4^0 + 7^3 + 2^8 + 4^8}{4^0 + 7^0 + 2^3 + 4^1} & 4736 := \frac{4^2 + 7^6 + 3^6 + 6^1}{4^2 + 7^1 + 3^0 + 6^0} \\
 4712 := \frac{4^3 + 7^4 - 1^0 + 2^{14}}{4^0 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 2^0} & 4724 := \frac{4^0 + 7^3 + 2^8 + 4^8}{4^0 + 7^0 + 2^3 + 4^1} & 4737 := \frac{4^6 + 7^8 + 3^{12} + 7^8}{4^2 + 7^0 + 3^7 + 7^3} \\
 4713 := \frac{4^4 + 7^6 + 1^0 - 3^4}{4^2 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 3^0} & 4725 := \frac{4^7 + 7^3 + 2^{11} + 5^3}{4^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 5^0} & 4737 := \frac{4^6 + 7^8 + 3^{12} + 7^8}{4^2 + 7^0 + 3^7 + 7^3} \\
 4714 := \frac{4^5 + 7^5 + 1^5 + 4^5}{4^0 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 4^0} & 4725 := \frac{4^7 + 7^3 + 2^{11} + 5^3}{4^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 5^0} & 4738 := \frac{4^8 + 7^0 + 3^9 + 8^2}{4^0 + 7^1 + 3^2 + 8^0} \\
 4714 := \frac{4^5 + 7^5 + 1^5 + 4^5}{4^0 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 4^0} & 4726 := \frac{-4^8 + 7^6 - 2^7 + 6^0}{4^0 + 7^0 + 2^3 + 6^0} & 4739 := \frac{4^2 + 7^6 + 3^4 + 9^3}{4^2 + 7^1 + 3^0 + 9^0} \\
 4714 := \frac{4^5 + 7^5 + 1^5 + 4^5}{4^0 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 4^0} & 4727 := \frac{4^1 + 7^2 + 2^{11} + 7^5}{4^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 7^0} & 4739 := \frac{4^2 + 7^6 + 3^4 + 9^3}{4^2 + 7^1 + 3^0 + 9^0} \\
 4715 := \frac{4^6 - 7^1 + 1^0 + 5^4}{4^1 - 7^0 - 1^0 - 5^0} & 4727 := \frac{4^1 + 7^2 + 2^{11} + 7^5}{4^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 7^0} & 4742 := \frac{4^0 + 7^5 + 4^7 + 2^1}{4^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 2^2} \\
 4716 := \frac{4^3 + 7^7 + 1^0 + 6^7}{4^2 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 6^3} & 4728 := \frac{4^0 + 7^1 + 2^{19} + 8^3}{4^3 + 7^1 + 2^5 + 8^1} & 4742 := \frac{4^0 + 7^5 + 4^7 + 2^1}{4^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 2^2} \\
 4716 := \frac{4^3 + 7^7 + 1^0 + 6^7}{4^2 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 6^3} & 4728 := \frac{4^0 + 7^1 + 2^{19} + 8^3}{4^3 + 7^1 + 2^5 + 8^1} & 4743 := \frac{4^0 + 7^5 + 4^7 + 3^2}{4^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 3^0} \\
 4717 := \frac{-4^4 - 7^4 + 1^0 + 7^5}{4^1 - 7^0 - 1^0 + 7^0} & 4729 := \frac{4^8 + 7^9 + 2^{11} + 9^5}{4^2 + 7^3 + 2^{13} + 9^1} & 4743 := \frac{4^0 + 7^5 + 4^7 + 3^2}{4^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 3^0} \\
 4718 := \frac{4^4 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 8^5}{4^1 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 8^0} & 4729 := \frac{4^8 + 7^9 + 2^{11} + 9^5}{4^2 + 7^3 + 2^{13} + 9^1} & 4744 := \frac{4^0 + 7^5 + 4^2 + 4^7}{4^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 4^1} \\
 4718 := \frac{4^4 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 8^5}{4^1 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 8^0} & 4730 := \frac{4^7 - 7^1 - 3^7 + 0^1}{4^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 0^1} & 4744 := \frac{4^0 + 7^5 + 4^2 + 4^7}{4^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 4^1} \\
 4720 := \frac{-4^6 + 7^6 + 2^{15} - 0^0}{4^2 + 7^1 + 2^3 + 0^1} & 4731 := \frac{4^2 + 7^5 + 3^{11} + 1^0}{-4^1 + 7^2 - 3^1 - 1^0} & 4745 := \frac{4^5 + 7^5 + 4^5 + 5^3}{4^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 5^0} \\
 4721 := \frac{4^{10} - 7^0 - 2^9 - 1^0}{4^2 - 7^2 + 2^8 - 1^0} & 4732 := \frac{4^3 + 7^5 + 3^2 + 2^{11}}{4^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 2^0} & 4745 := \frac{4^5 + 7^5 + 4^5 + 5^3}{4^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 5^0} \\
 4722 := \frac{4^0 + 7^5 + 2^5 + 2^{11}}{4^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 2^0} & 4733 := \frac{4^2 + 7^3 + 3^7 + 3^7}{4^1 - 7^0 - 3^0 - 3^0} & 4746 := \frac{4^4 - 7^4 + 4^7 - 6^0}{-4^0 - 7^0 - 4^0 + 6^1} \\
 4722 := \frac{4^0 + 7^5 + 2^5 + 2^{11}}{4^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 2^0} & 4734 := \frac{4^5 + 7^5 + 3^4 + 4^5}{4^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 4^0} & 4747 := \frac{4^0 + 7^0 + 4^5 + 7^6}{4^0 + 7^0 + 4^2 + 7^1}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 4747 := \frac{4^0 + 7^0 + 4^5 + 7^6}{4^0 + 7^0 + 4^2 + 7^1} & 4763 := \frac{4^0 - 7^2 + 6^5 + 3^8}{-4^0 - 7^0 + 6^1 - 3^0} & 4778 := \frac{-4^1 + 7^3 + 7^3 + 8^4}{-4^0 + 7^0 - 7^1 + 8^1} \\
 4748 := \frac{4^0 + 7^7 + 4^7 - 8^5}{4^0 - 7^3 + 4^5 - 8^3} & 4764 := \frac{4^0 + 7^5 - 6^5 + 4^{10}}{4^0 + 7^0 + 6^3 + 4^1} & 4779 := \frac{4^9 + 7^6 + 7^7 + 9^6}{4^1 + 7^1 + 7^3 + 9^1} \\
 4749 := \frac{4^3 + 7^5 + 4^3 + 9^5}{4^1 + 7^1 + 4^1 + 9^0} & 4765 := \frac{4^0 + 7^3 + 6^4 + 5^5}{4^0 + 7^0 - 6^1 + 5^1} & 4779 := \frac{4^9 + 7^6 + 7^7 + 9^6}{4^1 + 7^1 + 7^3 + 9^1} \\
 4749 := \frac{4^3 + 7^5 + 4^3 + 9^5}{4^1 + 7^1 + 4^1 + 9^0} & 4766 := \frac{-4^4 + 7^6 + 6^0 - 6^5}{4^1 + 7^1 + 6^1 + 6^1} & 4780 := \frac{-4^6 + 7^1 + 8^5 + 0^0}{4^1 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 0^1} \\
 4750 := \frac{-4^5 + 7^6 + 5^7 + 0^1}{-4^1 + 7^2 - 5^1 + 0^0} & 4767 := \frac{4^0 + 7^4 - 6^2 + 7^4}{-4^0 + 7^0 - 6^1 + 7^1} & 4782 := \frac{-4^2 + 7^7 + 8^0 - 2^{10}}{4^0 - 7^3 + 8^3 + 2^1} \\
 4752 := \frac{4^4 + 7^4 + 5^7 + 2^1}{4^0 + 7^1 + 5^0 + 2^3} & 4768 := \frac{4^0 - 7^4 + 6^5 + 8^5}{-4^0 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 8^0} & 4783 := \frac{4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 + 3^7}{4^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 3^0} \\
 4752 := \frac{4^4 + 7^4 + 5^7 + 2^1}{4^0 + 7^1 + 5^0 + 2^3} & 4769 := \frac{4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3}{4^0 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 9^0} & 4783 := \frac{4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 + 3^7}{4^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 3^0} \\
 4753 := \frac{4^5 + 7^6 + 5^3 + 3^3}{4^1 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 3^2} & 4769 := \frac{4^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 9^3}{4^0 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 9^0} & 4784 := \frac{-4^0 + 7^6 + 8^3 - 4^8}{4^0 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 4^0} \\
 4753 := \frac{4^5 + 7^6 + 5^3 + 3^3}{4^1 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 3^2} & 4772 := \frac{4^1 + 7^2 + 7^5 + 2^{17}}{4^0 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 2^4} & 4785 := \frac{4^4 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 5^7}{4^1 + 7^1 + 8^1 + 5^0} \\
 4754 := \frac{-4^2 + 7^2 + 5^4 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 7^0 - 5^0 + 4^1} & 4772 := \frac{4^1 + 7^2 + 7^5 + 2^{17}}{4^0 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 2^4} & 4785 := \frac{4^4 + 7^5 + 8^3 + 5^7}{4^1 + 7^1 + 8^1 + 5^0} \\
 4755 := \frac{-4^7 + 7^2 + 5^2 + 5^7}{4^1 + 7^1 + 5^0 + 5^0} & 4773 := \frac{4^4 + 7^3 + 7^4 + 3^{10}}{4^1 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 3^0} & 4786 := \frac{4^9 + 7^7 - 8^5 + 6^0}{4^1 - 7^0 + 8^0 + 6^3} \\
 4756 := \frac{4^6 - 7^0 + 5^4 + 6^2}{-4^0 + 7^0 - 5^1 + 6^1} & 4773 := \frac{4^4 + 7^3 + 7^4 + 3^{10}}{4^1 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 3^0} & 4787 := \frac{-4^2 + 7^4 + 8^0 + 7^4}{4^0 + 7^0 - 8^1 + 7^1} \\
 4757 := \frac{4^6 + 7^3 - 5^2 + 7^3}{4^1 - 7^0 - 5^0 - 7^0} & 4774 := \frac{-4^1 + 7^3 - 7^4 + 4^7}{-4^0 - 7^0 + 7^0 + 4^1} & 4788 := \frac{-4^2 + 7^7 + 8^0 + 8^1}{4^1 - 7^3 - 8^0 + 8^3} \\
 4758 := \frac{-4^4 + 7^4 + 5^5 - 8^3}{-4^0 - 7^0 - 5^1 + 8^1} & 4775 := \frac{4^8 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 5^6}{4^1 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 5^1} & 4789 := \frac{4^8 + 7^9 + 8^1 + 9^1}{4^5 + 7^3 + 8^3 + 9^4} \\
 4759 := \frac{4^8 + 7^7 + 5^3 + 9^3}{4^1 + 7^2 + 5^3 + 9^1} & 4775 := \frac{4^8 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 5^6}{4^1 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 5^1} & 4789 := \frac{4^8 + 7^9 + 8^1 + 9^1}{4^5 + 7^3 + 8^3 + 9^4} \\
 4759 := \frac{4^8 + 7^7 + 5^3 + 9^3}{4^1 + 7^2 + 5^3 + 9^1} & 4776 := \frac{4^6 + 7^2 + 7^5 + 6^7}{4^0 + 7^1 + 7^2 + 6^1} & 4790 := \frac{4^4 - 7^1 + 9^6 + 0^1}{4^3 + 7^2 - 9^0 - 0^0} \\
 4760 := \frac{4^8 + 7^4 - 6^4 - 0^0}{4^0 + 7^1 + 6^1 + 0^1} & 4776 := \frac{4^6 + 7^2 + 7^5 + 6^7}{4^0 + 7^1 + 7^2 + 6^1} & 4791 := \frac{4^2 + 7^3 + 9^6 + 1^0}{4^3 + 7^2 - 9^0 - 1^0} \\
 4762 := \frac{4^7 - 7^2 - 6^0 - 2^{11}}{-4^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 2^1} & 4777 := \frac{-4^3 + 7^6 - 7^7 + 7^8}{4^5 - 7^1 - 7^1 + 7^2} & 4792 := \frac{4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3 + 2^{11}}{4^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}
 \end{array}$$

$$4792 := \frac{4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3 + 2^{11}}{4^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4793 := \frac{4^5 + 7^2 + 9^5 + 3^7}{4^1 + 7^1 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4793 := \frac{4^5 + 7^2 + 9^5 + 3^7}{4^1 + 7^1 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4794 := \frac{4^1 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 4^9}{4^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 4^3}$$

$$4794 := \frac{4^1 + 7^0 + 9^5 + 4^9}{4^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 4^3}$$

$$4795 := \frac{4^6 - 7^1 + 9^2 + 5^4}{4^1 - 7^0 - 9^0 - 5^0}$$

$$4796 := \frac{4^6 + 7^1 + 9^3 - 6^2}{-4^0 - 7^0 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$4797 := \frac{4^5 + 7^0 + 9^6 + 7^0}{4^1 + 7^2 + 9^1 + 7^2}$$

$$4797 := \frac{4^5 + 7^0 + 9^6 + 7^0}{4^1 + 7^2 + 9^1 + 7^2}$$

$$4798 := \frac{4^7 + 7^3 + 9^4 - 8^4}{4^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4799 := \frac{4^9 + 7^3 + 9^3 + 9^3}{4^1 + 7^2 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4799 := \frac{4^9 + 7^3 + 9^3 + 9^3}{4^1 + 7^2 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4803 := \frac{4^6 + 8^4 + 0^0 + 3^{10}}{4^1 + 8^0 + 0^1 + 3^2}$$

$$4803 := \frac{4^6 + 8^4 + 0^0 + 3^{10}}{4^1 + 8^0 + 0^1 + 3^2}$$

$$4806 := \frac{4^{10} + 8^5 + 0^1 + 6^1}{4^0 + 8^1 + 0^1 + 6^3}$$

$$4806 := \frac{4^{10} + 8^5 + 0^1 + 6^1}{4^0 + 8^1 + 0^1 + 6^3}$$

$$4809 := \frac{-4^2 + 8^4 + 0^1 + 9^3}{-4^0 + 8^0 + 0^1 + 9^0}$$

$$4817 := \frac{4^2 + 8^6 - 1^0 - 7^6}{4^2 + 8^1 - 1^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4822 := \frac{4^1 - 8^4 + 2^8 + 2^{15}}{4^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 2^1}$$

$$4823 := \frac{4^4 + 8^1 + 2^{15} + 3^6}{4^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$4823 := \frac{4^4 + 8^1 + 2^{15} + 3^6}{4^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$4824 := \frac{4^2 - 8^4 + 2^{15} + 4^4}{-4^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$4825 := \frac{4^3 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 5^8}{4^1 + 8^1 + 2^6 + 5^1}$$

$$4825 := \frac{4^3 + 8^1 + 2^7 + 5^8}{4^1 + 8^1 + 2^6 + 5^1}$$

$$4826 := \frac{4^6 + 8^3 + 2^1 + 6^3}{-4^0 - 8^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$4827 := \frac{-4^1 + 8^5 + 2^{10} + 7^0}{4^0 + 8^0 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$4828 := \frac{4^1 + 8^3 + 2^9 + 8^5}{4^0 + 8^0 + 2^2 + 8^0}$$

$$4828 := \frac{4^1 + 8^3 + 2^9 + 8^5}{4^0 + 8^0 + 2^2 + 8^0}$$

$$4829 := \frac{4^5 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 9^1}{4^0 + 8^0 + 2^2 + 9^0}$$

$$4829 := \frac{4^5 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 9^1}{4^0 + 8^0 + 2^2 + 9^0}$$

$$4830 := \frac{4^1 + 8^4 + 3^6 + 0^0}{-4^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$$

$$4831 := \frac{-4^4 + 8^7 - 3^5 + 1^0}{4^1 + 8^3 - 3^4 - 1^0}$$

$$4832 := \frac{-4^0 + 8^1 + 3^6 + 2^{12}}{-4^0 - 8^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$4833 := \frac{4^0 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 3^{10}}{4^0 + 8^1 + 3^0 + 3^2}$$

$$4833 := \frac{4^0 + 8^5 + 3^2 + 3^{10}}{4^0 + 8^1 + 3^0 + 3^2}$$

$$4834 := \frac{4^0 + 8^1 + 3^6 + 4^6}{-4^0 - 8^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$4835 := \frac{4^4 + 8^1 - 3^{10} + 5^7}{4^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4836 := \frac{4^0 + 8^3 + 3^{12} + 6^1}{4^0 + 8^2 + 3^2 + 6^2}$$

$$4836 := \frac{4^0 + 8^3 + 3^{12} + 6^1}{4^0 + 8^2 + 3^2 + 6^2}$$

$$4837 := \frac{4^5 + 8^3 + 3^{10} + 7^5}{4^1 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 7^0}$$

$$4837 := \frac{4^5 + 8^3 + 3^{10} + 7^5}{4^1 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 7^0}$$

$$4838 := \frac{4^8 + 8^0 + 3^7 + 8^1}{4^1 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 8^1}$$

$$4838 := \frac{4^8 + 8^0 + 3^7 + 8^1}{4^1 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 8^1}$$

$$4839 := \frac{4^4 + 8^3 + 3^4 + 9^6}{4^0 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 9^2}$$

$$4839 := \frac{4^4 + 8^3 + 3^4 + 9^6}{4^0 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 9^2}$$

$$4841 := \frac{4^2 + 8^4 + 4^9 - 1^0}{-4^1 + 8^2 - 4^1 - 1^0}$$

$$4843 := \frac{-4^8 + 8^6 - 4^8 - 3^9}{-4^0 + 8^0 - 4^1 + 3^3}$$

$$4844 := \frac{4^2 + 8^7 + 4^8 + 4^8}{-4^1 + 8^3 + 4^2 - 4^3}$$

$$4845 := \frac{4^3 + 8^7 + 4^3 + 5^7}{4^1 + 8^2 + 4^4 + 5^3}$$

$$4845 := \frac{4^3 + 8^7 + 4^3 + 5^7}{4^1 + 8^2 + 4^4 + 5^3}$$

$$4846 := \frac{4^2 + 8^4 + 4^8 + 6^6}{4^0 + 8^0 + 4^2 + 6^1}$$

$$4846 := \frac{4^2 + 8^4 + 4^8 + 6^6}{4^0 + 8^0 + 4^2 + 6^1}$$

$$4847 := \frac{4^3 - 8^1 + 4^8 + 7^5}{4^0 + 8^1 + 4^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4848 := \frac{-4^2 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 8^4}{-4^0 - 8^0 + 4^1 - 8^0}$$

$4849 := \frac{4^7 + 8^3 + 4^8 + 9^0}{4^1 + 8^1 + 4^1 + 9^0}$	$4865 := \frac{-4^1 + 8^5 + 6^4 - 5^1}{4^1 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 5^0}$	$4879 := \frac{4^7 - 8^2 - 7^0 - 9^4}{-4^0 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$
$4850 := \frac{4^9 - 8^5 + 5^9 - 0^0}{-4^3 + 8^3 + 5^0 + 0^0}$	$4866 := \frac{-4^0 + 8^5 - 6^0 + 6^4}{4^1 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$	$4880 := \frac{-4^2 - 8^5 + 8^6 + 0^1}{-4^2 - 8^0 + 8^2 + 0^1}$
$4851 := \frac{4^1 - 8^3 + 5^7 - 1^0}{4^1 + 8^1 + 5^1 - 1^0}$	$4867 := \frac{4^1 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 7^0}{4^1 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 7^0}$	$4881 := \frac{4^7 - 8^2 + 8^7 + 1^0}{-4^2 - 8^2 + 8^3 + 1^0}$
$4852 := \frac{-4^0 + 8^5 + 5^6 + 2^7}{4^1 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 2^2}$	$4867 := \frac{4^1 + 8^5 + 6^4 + 7^0}{4^1 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 7^0}$	$4882 := \frac{4^1 - 8^3 + 8^5 + 2^{19}}{-4^2 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 2^7}$
$4853 := \frac{4^7 + 8^1 - 5^3 - 3^8}{-4^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$	$4868 := \frac{4^1 + 8^1 + 6^4 + 8^5}{4^1 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$	$4883 := \frac{4^5 - 8^2 + 8^5 + 3^{10}}{4^0 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 3^2}$
$4854 := \frac{-4^0 + 8^4 - 5^6 + 4^7}{-4^0 - 8^0 - 5^0 + 4^1}$	$4868 := \frac{4^1 + 8^1 + 6^4 + 8^5}{4^1 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$	$4884 := \frac{4^8 + 8^1 - 8^4 + 4^8}{4^0 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 4^2}$
$4855 := \frac{4^2 + 8^6 + 5^1 + 5^1}{4^2 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 5^2}$	$4869 := \frac{4^6 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 9^3}{-4^0 - 8^0 - 6^1 + 9^1}$	$4885 := \frac{4^{10} + 8^0 + 8^5 + 5^5}{4^4 - 8^0 - 8^1 - 5^2}$
$4855 := \frac{4^2 + 8^6 + 5^1 + 5^1}{4^2 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 5^2}$	$4870 := \frac{4^1 + 8^4 + 7^6 + 0^0}{4^2 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 0^0}$	$4886 := \frac{4^9 + 8^1 - 8^3 - 6^6}{-4^0 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 6^2}$
$4856 := \frac{4^7 + 8^4 - 5^6 + 6^0}{-4^0 + 8^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$	$4870 := \frac{4^1 + 8^4 + 7^6 + 0^0}{4^2 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 0^0}$	$4887 := \frac{4^7 + 8^1 + 8^7 + 7^7}{4^4 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 7^3}$
$4857 := \frac{4^8 + 8^0 + 5^1 - 7^4}{4^1 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 7^1}$	$4872 := \frac{-4^0 - 8^1 - 7^5 + 2^{16}}{4^0 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 2^0}$	$4887 := \frac{4^7 + 8^1 + 8^7 + 7^7}{4^4 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 7^3}$
$4858 := \frac{4^0 - 8^5 - 5^6 + 8^6}{4^1 + 8^0 - 5^2 + 8^2}$	$4873 := \frac{4^8 + 8^0 + 7^4 + 3^{12}}{4^0 + 8^2 + 7^2 + 3^2}$	$4888 := \frac{4^5 - 8^1 - 8^4 + 8^6}{-4^1 + 8^0 - 8^1 + 8^2}$
$4859 := \frac{4^7 + 8^1 + 5^5 - 9^2}{4^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$	$4873 := \frac{4^8 + 8^0 + 7^4 + 3^{12}}{4^0 + 8^2 + 7^2 + 3^2}$	$4889 := \frac{4^5 + 8^3 + 8^5 - 9^2}{4^1 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 9^0}$
$4860 := \frac{4^9 + 8^3 - 6^3 + 0^1}{4^2 + 8^0 + 6^2 + 0^0}$	$4874 := \frac{4^0 + 8^5 + 7^4 + 4^9}{-4^0 - 8^0 - 7^0 + 4^3}$	$4890 := \frac{4^3 + 8^4 + 9^3 + 0^0}{-4^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 0^1}$
$4862 := \frac{4^2 + 8^3 + 6^7 - 2^{13}}{4^1 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 2^3}$	$4875 := \frac{4^{12} + 8^1 + 7^4 + 5^7}{4^5 + 8^1 + 7^4 + 5^2}$	$4892 := \frac{4^0 + 8^7 - 9^4 - 2^{14}}{4^0 - 8^1 - 9^2 + 2^9}$
$4863 := \frac{4^5 + 8^5 + 6^1 + 3^5}{4^1 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$	$4875 := \frac{4^{12} + 8^1 + 7^4 + 5^7}{4^5 + 8^1 + 7^4 + 5^2}$	$4893 := \frac{4^7 - 8^2 - 9^4 + 3^3}{-4^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$
$4863 := \frac{4^5 + 8^5 + 6^1 + 3^5}{4^1 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$	$4876 := \frac{4^8 - 8^0 + 7^6 - 6^6}{-4^0 - 8^1 + 7^0 + 6^2}$	$4894 := \frac{-4^0 - 8^2 + 9^5 - 4^4}{4^0 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 4^0}$
$4864 := \frac{4^4 + 8^7 + 6^8 + 4^8}{4^2 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 4^4}$	$4877 := \frac{-4^4 - 8^4 + 7^5 + 7^5}{-4^0 - 8^0 + 7^0 + 7^1}$	$4895 := \frac{4^7 - 8^1 - 9^4 - 5^2}{-4^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 5^0}$
$4864 := \frac{4^4 + 8^7 + 6^8 + 4^8}{4^2 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 4^4}$	$4878 := \frac{-4^5 + 8^0 + 7^4 + 8^5}{4^1 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$	$4896 := \frac{-4^0 - 8^3 + 9^5 + 6^3}{4^0 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 6^0}$

$$4897 := \frac{-4^4 + 8^5 - 9^3 - 7^4}{-4^0 - 8^0 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4899 := \frac{4^7 + 8^5 - 9^2 - 9^2}{-4^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 9^1}$$

$$4902 := \frac{-4^4 + 9^5 - 0^0 + 2^5}{4^0 + 9^1 + 0^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4903 := \frac{-4^7 + 9^6 + 0^0 - 3^5}{-4^1 + 9^2 + 0^0 + 3^3}$$

$$4904 := \frac{-4^2 - 9^4 + 0^0 + 4^7}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4905 := \frac{4^8 + 9^1 + 0^1 + 5^5}{4^1 + 9^1 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$4905 := \frac{4^8 + 9^1 + 0^1 + 5^5}{4^1 + 9^1 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$4906 := \frac{-4^5 + 9^3 + 0^0 + 6^7}{4^3 - 9^0 + 0^1 - 6^1}$$

$$4908 := \frac{4^7 - 9^4 + 0^0 - 8^1}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4912 := \frac{4^7 - 9^4 - 1^0 + 2^1}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4913 := \frac{4^{10} + 9^2 - 1^0 - 3^7}{4^5 - 9^2 - 1^0 - 3^6}$$

$$4914 := \frac{4^1 - 9^4 + 1^0 + 4^7}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4916 := \frac{-4^3 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 6^1}{4^0 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4918 := \frac{4^6 + 9^4 + 1^0 + 8^4}{4^0 + 9^1 + 1^0 - 8^1}$$

$$4920 := \frac{4^2 - 9^4 + 2^{14} + 0^0}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 0^0}$$

$$4921 := \frac{4^0 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 1^0}{4^0 + 9^1 + 2^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4921 := \frac{4^0 + 9^5 + 2^0 + 1^0}{4^0 + 9^1 + 2^0 + 1^0}$$

$$4922 := \frac{4^0 + 9^7 + 2^{10} + 2^{20}}{4^2 + 9^2 + 2^6 + 2^{10}}$$

$$4922 := \frac{4^0 + 9^7 + 2^{10} + 2^{20}}{4^2 + 9^2 + 2^6 + 2^{10}}$$

$$4923 := \frac{4^1 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 3^9}{4^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4923 := \frac{4^1 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 3^9}{4^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4924 := \frac{-4^0 + 9^4 + 2^{15} + 4^3}{4^0 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$4925 := \frac{4^5 + 9^1 + 2^{13} + 5^4}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 5^0}$$

$$4926 := \frac{4^3 + 9^5 - 2^1 + 6^0}{4^0 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 6^1}$$

$$4927 := \frac{4^1 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 7^1}{4^0 + 9^1 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4927 := \frac{4^1 + 9^5 + 2^6 + 7^1}{4^0 + 9^1 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4928 := \frac{4^7 - 9^4 + 2^5 + 8^0}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4929 := \frac{4^2 + 9^2 + 2^1 + 9^5}{4^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 9^1}$$

$$4929 := \frac{4^2 + 9^2 + 2^1 + 9^5}{4^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 9^1}$$

$$4930 := \frac{-4^7 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 0^1}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 0^0}$$

$$4932 := \frac{4^1 + 9^1 + 3^9 + 2^5}{4^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4933 := \frac{4^0 + 9^5 + 3^7 + 3^{14}}{4^0 + 9^1 + 3^5 + 3^6}$$

$$4934 := \frac{4^{10} + 9^0 + 3^{15} + 4^{13}}{4^4 + 9^0 + 3^4 + 4^7}$$

$$4934 := \frac{4^{10} + 9^0 + 3^{15} + 4^{13}}{4^4 + 9^0 + 3^4 + 4^7}$$

$$4935 := \frac{4^{10} + 9^6 + 3^{13} + 5^9}{4^5 + 9^0 + 3^2 + 5^1}$$

$$4935 := \frac{4^{10} + 9^6 + 3^{13} + 5^9}{4^5 + 9^0 + 3^2 + 5^1}$$

$$4936 := \frac{4^2 + 9^1 + 3^9 + 6^2}{4^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4936 := \frac{4^2 + 9^1 + 3^9 + 6^2}{4^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$4937 := \frac{-4^5 - 9^3 - 3^5 + 7^5}{4^1 - 9^0 - 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4938 := \frac{4^1 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 8^2}{4^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4938 := \frac{4^1 + 9^0 + 3^9 + 8^2}{4^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4939 := \frac{4^0 - 9^1 + 3^9 + 9^2}{4^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4940 := \frac{4^9 - 9^4 + 4^{10} + 0^0}{-4^0 + 9^1 + 4^4 + 0^1}$$

$$4941 := \frac{-4^2 + 9^7 - 4^3 - 1^0}{-4^2 + 9^3 + 4^4 - 1^0}$$

$$4942 := \frac{4^0 + 9^5 + 4^4 - 2^1}{4^0 + 9^1 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4943 := \frac{4^1 + 9^2 + 4^1 + 3^9}{4^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4943 := \frac{4^1 + 9^2 + 4^1 + 3^9}{4^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4944 := \frac{4^0 - 9^4 + 4^3 + 4^7}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$4945 := \frac{-4^5 + 9^2 + 4^{11} - 5^0}{-4^4 + 9^2 + 4^5 - 5^0}$$

$$4946 := \frac{-4^0 + 9^0 + 4^9 - 6^1}{4^1 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 6^2}$$

$$4947 := \frac{4^3 - 9^4 + 4^7 + 7^1}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4948 := \frac{-4^0 + 9^5 - 4^7 - 8^5}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4949 := \frac{4^7 + 9^0 - 4^8 + 9^5}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4950 := \frac{4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 0^1}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$4951 := \frac{4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 1^0}{4^1 - 9^0 - 5^0 - 1^0}$$

$$4952 := \frac{4^5 + 9^2 + 5^7 + 2^1}{4^0 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 2^0}$$

$$4953 := \frac{4^8 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 3^{11}}{4^2 + 9^0 + 5^1 + 3^3}$$

$$4954 := \frac{4^2 + 9^5 + 5^7 + 4^7}{4^0 + 9^0 + 5^2 + 4^1}$$

$$4955 := \frac{4^6 + 9^3 + 5^1 + 5^3}{4^1 - 9^0 - 5^0 - 5^0}$$

$$4956 := \frac{4^2 + 9^6 + 5^7 + 6^1}{4^0 + 9^2 + 5^1 + 6^2}$$

$$4957 := \frac{4^7 + 9^6 + 5^0 + 7^4}{4^1 + 9^2 + 5^2 + 7^0}$$

$$4958 := \frac{4^6 + 9^3 + 5^3 + 8^1}{-4^0 - 9^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$4959 := \frac{4^5 + 9^2 + 5^5 + 9^3}{4^1 - 9^0 - 5^0 - 9^0}$$

$$4960 := \frac{4^9 + 9^3 + 6^1 + 0^0}{4^2 + 9^0 + 6^2 + 0^1}$$

$$4960 := \frac{4^9 + 9^3 + 6^1 + 0^0}{4^2 + 9^0 + 6^2 + 0^1}$$

$$4962 := \frac{4^0 + 9^5 + 6^8 + 2^{15}}{4^1 + 9^1 + 6^3 + 2^7}$$

$$4962 := \frac{4^0 + 9^5 + 6^8 + 2^{15}}{4^1 + 9^1 + 6^3 + 2^7}$$

$$4963 := \frac{4^3 + 9^7 + 6^4 + 3^1}{4^2 + 9^3 + 6^3 + 3^1}$$

$$4963 := \frac{4^3 + 9^7 + 6^4 + 3^1}{4^2 + 9^3 + 6^3 + 3^1}$$

$$4964 := \frac{-4^6 + 9^2 - 6^0 + 4^9}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 6^2 + 4^2}$$

$$4965 := \frac{4^{12} + 9^7 + 6^5 - 5^0}{4^1 - 9^2 + 6^4 + 5^5}$$

$$4966 := \frac{-4^0 + 9^5 - 6^4 + 6^7}{-4^0 + 9^2 - 6^1 - 6^1}$$

$$4967 := \frac{4^7 + 9^0 + 6^7 + 7^9}{4^3 + 9^0 + 6^5 + 7^3}$$

$$4967 := \frac{4^7 + 9^0 + 6^7 + 7^9}{4^3 + 9^0 + 6^5 + 7^3}$$

$$4968 := \frac{4^8 - 9^2 + 6^0 + 8^4}{4^1 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 8^1}$$

$$4969 := \frac{4^0 - 9^2 + 6^7 - 9^4}{4^0 + 9^1 + 6^2 + 9^1}$$

$$4971 := \frac{4^3 + 9^4 + 7^6 + 1^0}{4^2 + 9^0 + 7^1 + 1^0}$$

$$4971 := \frac{4^3 + 9^4 + 7^6 + 1^0}{4^2 + 9^0 + 7^1 + 1^0}$$

$$4972 := \frac{4^5 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 2^{11}}{4^0 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4972 := \frac{4^5 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 2^{11}}{4^0 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$4973 := \frac{4^4 + 9^4 + 7^3 - 3^7}{4^1 - 9^0 - 7^0 - 3^0}$$

$$4974 := \frac{4^4 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 4^7}{4^0 + 9^1 + 7^0 + 4^2}$$

$$4974 := \frac{4^4 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 4^7}{4^0 + 9^1 + 7^0 + 4^2}$$

$$4975 := \frac{4^7 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 5^7}{4^1 + 9^1 + 7^0 + 5^1}$$

$$4975 := \frac{4^7 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 5^7}{4^1 + 9^1 + 7^0 + 5^1}$$

$$4976 := \frac{4^7 + 9^3 - 7^4 + 6^3}{-4^0 - 9^0 - 7^0 + 6^1}$$

$$4977 := \frac{4^4 - 9^2 + 7^4 + 7^4}{4^1 - 9^0 - 7^0 - 7^0}$$

$$4978 := \frac{4^{11} + 9^3 + 7^1 + 8^7}{4^2 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 8^3}$$

$$4978 := \frac{4^{11} + 9^3 + 7^1 + 8^7}{4^2 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 8^3}$$

$$4979 := \frac{4^4 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 9^4}{4^2 + 9^0 + 7^1 + 9^0}$$

$$4979 := \frac{4^4 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 9^4}{4^2 + 9^0 + 7^1 + 9^0}$$

$$4982 := \frac{4^0 + 9^6 + 8^7 - 2^{18}}{4^0 + 9^3 + 8^0 - 2^8}$$

$$4983 := \frac{4^4 + 9^0 - 8^1 + 3^9}{4^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$4984 := \frac{-4^2 - 9^3 + 8^0 + 4^8}{-4^0 - 9^0 - 8^0 + 4^2}$$

$$4985 := \frac{4^8 + 9^6 + 8^5 + 5^7}{4^3 + 9^1 + 8^2 + 5^1}$$

$$4985 := \frac{4^8 + 9^6 + 8^5 + 5^7}{4^3 + 9^1 + 8^2 + 5^1}$$

$$4986 := \frac{4^8 + 9^7 + 8^6 + 6^0}{4^2 + 9^3 + 8^2 + 6^3}$$

$$4986 := \frac{4^8 + 9^7 + 8^6 + 6^0}{4^2 + 9^3 + 8^2 + 6^3}$$

$$4987 := \frac{4^5 - 9^3 + 8^5 + 7^5}{4^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 7^1}$$

$$4988 := \frac{4^7 + 9^3 - 8^0 + 8^5}{-4^0 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$4989 := \frac{-4^7 + 9^2 - 8^5 + 9^5}{-4^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$4992 := \frac{-4^6 - 9^1 + 9^5 - 2^5}{4^0 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 2^3}$$

$$4993 := \frac{4^5 + 9^1 + 9^4 + 3^{11}}{4^2 + 9^1 + 9^1 + 3^1}$$

$$4993 := \frac{4^5 + 9^1 + 9^4 + 3^{11}}{4^2 + 9^1 + 9^1 + 3^1}$$

$$4994 := \frac{-4^3 - 9^2 + 9^5 + 4^5}{4^0 + 9^0 + 9^1 + 4^0}$$

$$4995 := \frac{-4^6 - 9^1 + 9^5 + 5^0}{4^1 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 5^1}$$

$$4996 := \frac{4^6 + 9^5 + 9^7 + 6^1}{4^2 + 9^1 + 9^3 + 6^3}$$

$$4996 := \frac{4^6 + 9^5 + 9^7 + 6^1}{4^2 + 9^1 + 9^3 + 6^3}$$

$$4997 := \frac{4^9 - 9^3 - 9^4 - 7^1}{4^1 - 9^0 - 9^0 + 7^2}$$

$$4998 := \frac{4^7 - 9^3 - 9^4 - 8^4}{4^0 + 9^0 - 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$4999 := \frac{4^2 - 9^0 - 9^4 + 9^6}{4^2 - 9^0 + 9^1 + 9^2}$$

$$5022 := \frac{5^1 + 0^0 - 2^8 + 2^{16}}{5^0 + 0^1 + 2^2 + 2^3}$$

$$5023 := \frac{5^9 + 0^0 + 2^{11} + 3^{10}}{5^3 + 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^5}$$

$$5023 := \frac{5^9 + 0^0 + 2^{11} + 3^{10}}{5^3 + 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^5}$$

$$5024 := \frac{5^8 - 0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7}{5^0 + 0^1 + 2^4 + 4^3}$$

$$5025 := \frac{-5^4 - 0^0 + 2^{20} - 5^7}{5^1 - 0^0 + 2^6 + 5^3}$$

$$5026 := \frac{5^6 + 0^0 - 2^9 - 6^2}{5^0 + 0^1 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$5027 := \frac{5^8 + 0^1 + 2^{19} + 7^0}{5^1 + 0^1 + 2^7 + 7^2}$$

$$5027 := \frac{5^8 + 0^1 + 2^{19} + 7^0}{5^1 + 0^1 + 2^7 + 7^2}$$

$$5028 := \frac{-5^4 + 0^0 - 2^6 + 8^6}{-5^1 + 0^0 - 2^3 + 8^2}$$

$$5029 := \frac{5^0 + 0^0 + 2^{14} + 9^5}{5^0 + 0^0 + 2^2 + 9^1}$$

$$5029 := \frac{5^0 + 0^0 + 2^{14} + 9^5}{5^0 + 0^0 + 2^2 + 9^1}$$

$$5032 := \frac{5^8 + 0^1 - 3^0 - 2^{13}}{-5^0 + 0^1 + 3^4 - 2^2}$$

$$5033 := \frac{5^4 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 3^{15}}{5^5 + 0^1 - 3^3 - 3^5}$$

$$5034 := \frac{5^5 + 0^1 - 3^7 + 4^6}{-5^0 - 0^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5035 := \frac{-5^0 - 0^0 - 3^9 + 5^9}{5^0 + 0^0 - 3^5 + 5^4}$$

$$5036 := \frac{5^8 + 0^1 + 3^{11} + 6^4}{5^2 + 0^0 + 3^4 + 6^1}$$

$$5036 := \frac{5^8 + 0^1 + 3^{11} + 6^4}{5^2 + 0^0 + 3^4 + 6^1}$$

$$5037 := \frac{5^1 + 0^1 + 3^{13} + 7^4}{5^2 + 0^1 + 3^5 + 7^2}$$

$$5037 := \frac{5^1 + 0^1 + 3^{13} + 7^4}{5^2 + 0^1 + 3^5 + 7^2}$$

$$5038 := \frac{5^3 + 0^1 + 3^{11} + 8^4}{5^0 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 8^1}$$

$$5038 := \frac{5^3 + 0^1 + 3^{11} + 8^4}{5^0 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 8^1}$$

$$5039 := \frac{5^9 - 0^0 + 3^{13} + 9^1}{5^0 + 0^0 - 3^3 + 9^3}$$

$$5041 := \frac{-5^0 - 0^0 + 4^8 - 1^0}{-5^0 - 0^0 + 4^2 - 1^0}$$

$$5042 := \frac{5^0 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^3}{5^0 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 2^3}$$

$$5042 := \frac{5^0 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 2^3}{5^0 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 2^3}$$

$$5043 := \frac{5^3 + 0^1 + 4^{10} + 3^5}{5^3 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 3^4}$$

$$5043 := \frac{5^3 + 0^1 + 4^{10} + 3^5}{5^3 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 3^4}$$

$$5045 := \frac{-5^4 + 0^0 + 4^7 - 5^4}{5^0 + 0^1 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$5046 := \frac{5^2 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 6^2}{5^1 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$5046 := \frac{5^2 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 6^2}{5^1 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$5047 := \frac{5^5 + 0^1 + 4^4 + 7^5}{5^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5047 := \frac{5^5 + 0^1 + 4^4 + 7^5}{5^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5048 := \frac{5^2 - 0^0 + 4^8 + 8^2}{5^0 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 8^1}$$

$$5049 := \frac{-5^3 + 0^0 + 4^{11} - 9^5}{5^2 + 0^0 + 4^3 + 9^3}$$

$$5062 := \frac{-5^5 + 0^0 - 6^1 + 2^{13}}{-5^0 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5063 := \frac{5^7 + 0^0 + 6^1 - 3^7}{5^1 + 0^0 + 6^1 + 3^1}$$

$$5068 := \frac{-5^0 + 0^0 + 6^5 + 8^5}{5^0 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 8^0}$$

$$5069 := \frac{5^0 + 0^0 + 6^8 + 9^5}{5^3 + 0^0 + 6^3 + 9^0}$$

$$5069 := \frac{5^0 + 0^0 + 6^8 + 9^5}{5^3 + 0^0 + 6^3 + 9^0}$$

$$5072 := \frac{5^8 + 0^1 - 7^2 - 2^5}{5^1 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 2^6}$$

$$5073 := \frac{5^6 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 3^{11}}{-5^0 - 0^0 + 7^2 - 3^2}$$

$$5074 := \frac{5^{11} + 0^1 + 7^0 - 4^5}{5^5 + 0^0 + 7^4 + 4^6}$$

$$5075 := \frac{5^5 - 0^0 - 7^2 + 5^7}{-5^0 - 0^0 - 7^1 + 5^2}$$

$$5076 := \frac{-5^2 + 0^1 + 7^4 + 6^5}{-5^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$5078 := \frac{5^9 + 0^1 - 7^1 - 8^6}{-5^0 - 0^0 + 7^3 - 8^1}$$

$$5082 := \frac{-5^4 - 0^0 - 8^3 + 2^{14}}{5^0 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$5083 := \frac{5^4 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 3^7}{5^1 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$5083 := \frac{5^4 + 0^0 + 8^5 + 3^7}{5^1 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$5086 := \frac{5^8 + 0^0 - 8^4 + 6^1}{5^1 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 6^1}$$

$$5092 := \frac{5^5 + 0^1 - 9^2 + 2^{11}}{-5^0 - 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5095 := \frac{5^7 - 0^0 - 9^1 + 8^8}{5^1 + 0^0 + 9^2 + 8^1}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 5097 := \frac{5^6 + 0^1 + 9^1 - 7^3}{5^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 7^0} & 5143 := \frac{5^6 + 1^0 + 4^{11} + 3^7}{5^2 + 1^0 + 4^3 + 3^6} & 5185 := \frac{-5^1 - 1^0 - 8^2 + 5^6}{-5^0 + 1^0 + 8^1 - 5^1} \\
 5098 := \frac{-5^4 + 0^1 - 9^6 + 8^7}{-5^3 + 0^0 - 9^2 + 8^3} & 5144 := \frac{5^2 - 1^0 + 4^5 + 4^6}{-5^0 - 1^0 - 4^0 + 4^1} & 5186 := \frac{5^2 + 1^0 - 8^1 + 6^6}{5^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 6^1} \\
 5122 := \frac{5^0 + 1^0 + 2^{10} + 2^{12}}{-5^0 - 1^0 + 2^0 + 2^1} & 5145 := \frac{-5^3 - 1^0 - 4^3 + 5^6}{-5^0 - 1^0 + 4^1 + 5^0} & 5187 := \frac{5^6 - 1^0 - 8^2 + 7^0}{5^0 + 1^0 + 8^1 - 7^1} \\
 5123 := \frac{5^6 - 1^0 - 2^8 + 3^0}{-5^0 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 3^0} & 5146 := \frac{5^8 - 1^0 + 4^4 + 6^3}{5^1 + 1^0 + 4^3 + 6^1} & 5193 := \frac{5^9 + 1^0 + 9^4 - 3^{10}}{5^3 - 1^0 - 9^0 + 3^5} \\
 5124 := \frac{5^1 - 1^0 + 2^{10} + 4^6}{-5^0 - 1^0 - 2^0 + 4^1} & 5153 := \frac{-5^6 + 1^0 + 5^9 + 3^3}{-5^1 - 1^0 + 5^4 - 3^5} & 5195 := \frac{5^6 + 1^0 - 9^2 + 5^6}{-5^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 5^1} \\
 5125 := \frac{5^1 + 1^0 - 2^8 + 5^6}{-5^0 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 5^0} & 5159 := \frac{5^5 - 1^0 - 5^8 + 9^7}{-5^0 - 1^0 + 5^3 + 9^3} & 5197 := \frac{-5^0 + 1^0 + 9^5 + 7^6}{5^2 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 7^1} \\
 5126 := \frac{5^6 + 1^0 - 2^5 - 6^3}{-5^0 - 1^0 - 2^0 + 6^1} & 5162 := \frac{-5^5 - 1^0 + 6^5 + 2^9}{-5^0 - 1^0 + 6^0 + 2^1} & 5201 := \frac{-5^5 + 2^{16} + 0^1 + 1^0}{5^1 + 2^3 + 0^1 - 1^0} \\
 5127 := \frac{5^9 - 1^0 + 2^8 + 7^1}{5^1 + 1^0 + 2^5 + 7^3} & 5163 := \frac{5^6 - 1^0 - 6^3 + 3^4}{-5^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 - 3^0} & 5202 := \frac{5^6 - 2^1 - 0^0 - 2^4}{5^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 2^0} \\
 5128 := \frac{5^5 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 8^5}{5^0 + 1^0 + 2^2 + 8^0} & 5165 := \frac{-5^3 + 1^0 - 6^1 + 5^6}{-5^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 - 5^0} & 5203 := \frac{5^9 + 2^{17} + 0^0 + 3^{13}}{5^4 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 3^4} \\
 5128 := \frac{5^5 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 8^5}{5^0 + 1^0 + 2^2 + 8^0} & 5166 := \frac{-5^6 + 1^0 - 6^2 + 6^6}{5^1 - 1^0 + 6^0 + 6^0} & 5203 := \frac{5^9 + 2^{17} + 0^0 + 3^{13}}{5^4 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 3^4} \\
 5129 := \frac{5^5 + 1^0 + 2^{15} + 9^1}{5^0 + 1^0 + 2^2 + 9^0} & 5167 := \frac{5^9 - 1^0 - 6^8 + 7^3}{-5^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 + 7^2} & 5204 := \frac{5^6 + 2^1 + 0^0 - 4^2}{5^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 4^0} \\
 5129 := \frac{5^5 + 1^0 + 2^{15} + 9^1}{5^0 + 1^0 + 2^2 + 9^0} & 5169 := \frac{5^6 - 1^0 - 6^2 - 9^2}{-5^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 - 9^0} & 5205 := \frac{-5^0 - 2^3 - 0^0 + 5^6}{5^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 5^0} \\
 5134 := \frac{5^4 - 1^0 + 3^{15} - 4^0}{5^4 - 1^0 + 3^7 - 4^2} & 5173 := \frac{5^4 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 3^{10}}{5^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 3^2} & 5206 := \frac{5^6 - 2^0 + 0^1 - 6^1}{5^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 6^0} \\
 5135 := \frac{5^8 - 1^0 - 3^6 + 5^8}{5^2 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 5^3} & 5173 := \frac{5^4 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 3^{10}}{5^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 3^2} & 5207 := \frac{5^6 - 2^1 - 0^0 - 7^0}{5^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 7^0} \\
 5137 := \frac{5^8 + 1^0 + 3^7 - 7^4}{5^2 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 7^2} & 5175 := \frac{-5^6 + 1^0 - 7^4 + 5^8}{-5^0 - 1^0 + 7^2 + 5^2} & 5208 := \frac{5^6 - 2^0 - 0^0 + 8^0}{5^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 8^0} \\
 5140 := \frac{5^7 - 1^0 - 4^5 + 0^1}{-5^0 - 1^0 + 4^2 + 0^0} & 5182 := \frac{5^5 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 2^{11}}{-5^0 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 2^1} & 5209 := \frac{5^6 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 9^0}{5^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 9^0} \\
 5142 := \frac{5^6 + 1^0 - 4^1 + 2^{19}}{-5^2 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 2^7} & 5183 := \frac{5^0 + 1^0 + 8^6 + 3^7}{-5^1 + 1^0 + 8^2 - 3^2} & 5209 := \frac{5^6 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 9^0}{5^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 9^0} \\
 5143 := \frac{5^6 + 1^0 + 4^{11} + 3^7}{5^2 + 1^0 + 4^3 + 3^6} & 5184 := \frac{5^6 - 1^0 - 8^1 - 4^3}{-5^0 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 4^1} & 5210 := \frac{5^6 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 0^1}{5^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 0^1}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 5210 := \frac{5^6 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 0^1}{5^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 0^1} & 5224 := \frac{5^6 - 2^0 - 2^4 + 4^3}{-5^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 4^1} & 5235 := \frac{5^3 + 2^5 + 3^5 + 5^7}{5^1 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 5^1} \\
 5211 := \frac{5^6 + 2^3 - 1^0 + 1^0}{-5^0 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 1^0} & 5225 := \frac{5^4 + 2^2 + 2^{12} + 5^{11}}{5^1 + 2^{10} + 2^{13} + 5^3} & 5235 := \frac{5^3 + 2^5 + 3^5 + 5^7}{5^1 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 5^1} \\
 5212 := \frac{5^6 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 2^3}{-5^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 2^1} & 5225 := \frac{5^4 + 2^2 + 2^{12} + 5^{11}}{5^1 + 2^{10} + 2^{13} + 5^3} & 5236 := \frac{5^7 + 2^{17} + 3^3 + 6^3}{5^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 6^2} \\
 5213 := \frac{5^6 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 3^2}{-5^0 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 3^0} & 5226 := \frac{5^7 + 2^3 + 2^8 + 6^0}{5^1 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 6^1} & 5236 := \frac{5^7 + 2^{17} + 3^3 + 6^3}{5^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 6^2} \\
 5214 := \frac{5^6 + 2^1 - 1^0 + 4^2}{-5^0 - 2^0 + 1^0 + 4^1} & 5226 := \frac{5^7 + 2^3 + 2^8 + 6^0}{5^1 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 6^1} & 5237 := \frac{5^1 + 2^{12} + 3^9 + 7^4}{5^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 7^0} \\
 5215 := \frac{5^1 + 2^4 - 1^0 + 5^6}{-5^0 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 5^0} & 5227 := \frac{5^0 + 2^2 + 2^{12} + 7^5}{5^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0} & 5237 := \frac{5^1 + 2^{12} + 3^9 + 7^4}{5^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 7^0} \\
 5216 := \frac{5^6 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 6^1}{-5^0 - 2^0 - 1^0 + 6^1} & 5227 := \frac{5^0 + 2^2 + 2^{12} + 7^5}{5^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0} & 5238 := \frac{5^4 + 2^8 + 3^{11} + 8^2}{5^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 8^1} \\
 5217 := \frac{5^7 + 2^7 + 1^0 + 7^0}{5^1 + 2^1 + 1^1 + 7^1} & 5228 := \frac{5^6 - 2^0 - 2^2 + 8^2}{-5^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 8^0} & 5238 := \frac{5^4 + 2^8 + 3^{11} + 8^2}{5^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 8^1} \\
 5217 := \frac{5^7 + 2^7 + 1^0 + 7^0}{5^1 + 2^1 + 1^1 + 7^1} & 5229 := \frac{5^8 + 2^2 + 2^4 + 9^5}{5^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 9^2} & 5239 := \frac{5^5 + 2^{14} + 3^3 + 9^5}{5^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 9^1} \\
 5218 := \frac{-5^8 + 2^{20} + 1^0 + 8^7}{-5^0 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 8^3} & 5229 := \frac{5^8 + 2^2 + 2^4 + 9^5}{5^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 9^2} & 5239 := \frac{5^5 + 2^{14} + 3^3 + 9^5}{5^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 9^1} \\
 5219 := \frac{5^0 + 2^{14} + 1^0 - 9^3}{-5^0 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 9^0} & 5230 := \frac{5^6 + 2^6 + 3^0 + 0^1}{5^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 0^1} & 5240 := \frac{5^6 + 2^5 + 4^3 - 0^0}{5^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 0^1} \\
 5220 := \frac{5^6 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 0^0}{5^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 0^1} & 5230 := \frac{5^6 + 2^6 + 3^0 + 0^1}{5^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 0^1} & 5241 := \frac{-5^3 + 2^5 + 4^9 - 1^0}{5^0 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 1^0} \\
 5220 := \frac{5^6 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 0^0}{5^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 0^1} & 5231 := \frac{5^6 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 1^0}{-5^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 1^0} & 5242 := \frac{5^{10} + 2^0 + 4^9 + 2^{20}}{5^0 + 2^6 + 4^5 + 2^{10}} \\
 5221 := \frac{5^3 + 2^{14} + 2^{20} - 1^0}{5^3 + 2^4 + 2^6 - 1^0} & 5232 := \frac{5^5 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 2^{15}}{5^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 2^2} & 5242 := \frac{5^{10} + 2^0 + 4^9 + 2^{20}}{5^0 + 2^6 + 4^5 + 2^{10}} \\
 5222 := \frac{5^8 + 2^0 + 2^9 + 2^9}{5^0 + 2^1 + 2^3 + 2^6} & 5232 := \frac{5^5 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 2^{15}}{5^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 2^2} & 5243 := \frac{5^0 + 2^{17} + 4^0 + 3^0}{5^1 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 3^1} \\
 5222 := \frac{5^8 + 2^0 + 2^9 + 2^9}{5^0 + 2^1 + 2^3 + 2^6} & 5233 := \frac{5^5 + 2^{15} + 3^2 + 3^6}{5^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 3^1} & 5243 := \frac{5^0 + 2^{17} + 4^0 + 3^0}{5^1 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 3^1} \\
 5223 := \frac{5^0 + 2^{10} + 2^{16} + 3^8}{5^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 3^2} & 5233 := \frac{5^5 + 2^{15} + 3^2 + 3^6}{5^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 3^1} & 5244 := \frac{5^3 - 2^0 + 4^5 + 4^6}{-5^0 - 2^0 - 4^0 + 4^1} \\
 5223 := \frac{5^0 + 2^{10} + 2^{16} + 3^8}{5^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 3^2} & 5234 := \frac{5^5 + 2^{15} + 3^6 + 4^2}{5^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 4^1} & 5245 := \frac{5^4 + 2^{10} + 4^{12} + 5^6}{5^1 + 2^3 + 4^3 + 5^5}
 \end{array}$$

$$5245 := \frac{5^4 + 2^{10} + 4^{12} + 5^6}{5^1 + 2^3 + 4^3 + 5^5}$$

$$5246 := \frac{5^3 + 2^{10} + 4^6 + 6^0}{-5^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 - 6^0}$$

$$5247 := \frac{5^5 + 2^5 + 4^5 + 7^5}{5^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5247 := \frac{5^5 + 2^5 + 4^5 + 7^5}{5^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5247 := \frac{5^5 + 2^5 + 4^5 + 7^5}{5^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5248 := \frac{-5^4 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 8^0}{-5^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 + 8^0}$$

$$5249 := \frac{5^6 + 2^{15} + 4^6 + 9^0}{5^0 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5249 := \frac{5^6 + 2^{15} + 4^6 + 9^0}{5^0 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5250 := \frac{5^3 - 2^0 + 5^6 + 0^0}{5^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$5251 := \frac{5^3 + 2^1 + 5^6 + 1^0}{-5^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$5252 := \frac{5^2 + 2^1 + 5^7 + 2^{14}}{5^0 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 2^3}$$

$$5252 := \frac{5^2 + 2^1 + 5^7 + 2^{14}}{5^0 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 2^3}$$

$$5253 := \frac{5^2 + 2^{12} + 5^6 + 3^{10}}{5^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 3^1}$$

$$5253 := \frac{5^2 + 2^{12} + 5^6 + 3^{10}}{5^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 3^1}$$

$$5254 := \frac{5^7 + 2^{10} + 5^9 + 4^5}{5^1 + 2^0 + 5^3 + 4^4}$$

$$5254 := \frac{5^7 + 2^{10} + 5^9 + 4^5}{5^1 + 2^0 + 5^3 + 4^4}$$

$$5255 := \frac{-5^0 + 2^4 + 5^3 + 5^6}{-5^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$5256 := \frac{5^2 + 2^{18} + 5^4 + 6^1}{5^0 + 2^3 + 5^1 + 6^2}$$

$$5256 := \frac{5^2 + 2^{18} + 5^4 + 6^1}{5^0 + 2^3 + 5^1 + 6^2}$$

$$5257 := \frac{5^1 + 2^{17} + 5^1 + 7^3}{5^0 + 2^4 + 5^0 + 7^1}$$

$$5257 := \frac{5^1 + 2^{17} + 5^1 + 7^3}{5^0 + 2^4 + 5^0 + 7^1}$$

$$5258 := \frac{5^2 + 2^9 + 5^4 + 8^4}{-5^0 - 2^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$5259 := \frac{5^1 + 2^{11} + 5^5 + 9^2}{5^0 - 2^1 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$5261 := \frac{5^9 + 2^6 - 6^8 - 1^0}{-5^0 + 2^4 + 6^2 + 1^0}$$

$$5262 := \frac{5^9 + 2^5 + 6^0 + 2^{18}}{5^0 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 2^8}$$

$$5262 := \frac{5^9 + 2^5 + 6^0 + 2^{18}}{5^0 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 2^8}$$

$$5263 := \frac{5^1 + 2^{12} + 6^1 + 3^{10}}{5^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 3^2}$$

$$5263 := \frac{5^1 + 2^{12} + 6^1 + 3^{10}}{5^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 3^2}$$

$$5264 := \frac{-5^4 + 2^5 + 6^0 + 4^7}{-5^0 - 2^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5265 := \frac{5^2 + 2^6 + 6^8 + 5^6}{5^1 + 2^8 + 6^2 + 5^2}$$

$$5265 := \frac{5^2 + 2^6 + 6^8 + 5^6}{5^1 + 2^8 + 6^2 + 5^2}$$

$$5266 := \frac{-5^3 + 2^{12} - 6^0 + 6^4}{5^0 - 2^1 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$5267 := \frac{5^1 + 2^{19} + 6^1 + 7^4}{5^2 + 2^5 + 6^2 + 7^1}$$

$$5267 := \frac{5^1 + 2^{19} + 6^1 + 7^4}{5^2 + 2^5 + 6^2 + 7^1}$$

$$5268 := \frac{-5^3 + 2^0 + 6^4 + 8^4}{5^0 - 2^1 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$5269 := \frac{5^0 + 2^{18} + 6^4 + 9^1}{5^0 + 2^2 + 6^2 + 9^1}$$

$$5269 := \frac{5^0 + 2^{18} + 6^4 + 9^1}{5^0 + 2^2 + 6^2 + 9^1}$$

$$5270 := \frac{5^5 + 2^{15} + 7^5 + 0^1}{5^0 + 2^0 + 7^1 + 0^0}$$

$$5270 := \frac{5^5 + 2^{15} + 7^5 + 0^1}{5^0 + 2^0 + 7^1 + 0^0}$$

$$5271 := \frac{5^5 - 2^8 + 7^4 + 1^0}{5^0 - 2^1 + 7^0 + 1^0}$$

$$5272 := \frac{5^6 + 2^{10} + 7^3 + 2^{12}}{5^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$5272 := \frac{5^6 + 2^{10} + 7^3 + 2^{12}}{5^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$5273 := \frac{5^0 + 2^{15} + 7^0 + 3^{12}}{5^2 + 2^5 + 7^2 + 3^0}$$

$$5273 := \frac{5^0 + 2^{15} + 7^0 + 3^{12}}{5^2 + 2^5 + 7^2 + 3^0}$$

$$5274 := \frac{5^1 + 2^{15} + 7^2 + 4^6}{5^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5274 := \frac{5^1 + 2^{15} + 7^2 + 4^6}{5^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5275 := \frac{5^4 + 2^5 + 7^3 + 5^7}{5^0 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 5^1}$$

$$5275 := \frac{5^4 + 2^5 + 7^3 + 5^7}{5^0 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 5^1}$$

$$5276 := \frac{5^6 + 2^{10} + 7^1 + 6^6}{5^0 + 2^2 + 7^0 + 6^1}$$

$$5277 := \frac{5^9 + 2^3 + 7^8 + 7^8}{5^2 + 2^7 + 7^0 + 7^4}$$

$$5277 := \frac{5^9 + 2^3 + 7^8 + 7^8}{5^2 + 2^7 + 7^0 + 7^4}$$

$$5278 := \frac{5^4 + 2^{14} + 7^1 + 8^4}{5^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$5278 := \frac{5^4 + 2^{14} + 7^1 + 8^4}{5^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$5279 := \frac{5^3 + 2^{17} + 7^2 + 9^3}{5^0 + 2^3 + 7^1 + 9^1}$$

$$5279 := \frac{5^3 + 2^{17} + 7^2 + 9^3}{5^0 + 2^3 + 7^1 + 9^1}$$

$$5280 := \frac{5^8 - 2^{12} - 8^5 - 0^0}{5^0 + 2^0 + 8^2 + 0^0}$$

$$5282 := \frac{5^5 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 2^{16}}{5^0 + 2^1 + 8^1 + 2^1}$$

$$5282 := \frac{5^5 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 2^{16}}{5^0 + 2^1 + 8^1 + 2^1}$$

$$5283 := \frac{5^4 + 2^{14} + 8^4 + 3^3}{5^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$5283 := \frac{5^4 + 2^{14} + 8^4 + 3^3}{5^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$5284 := \frac{5^3 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 4^6}{5^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5285 := \frac{5^3 + 2^{10} + 8^0 + 5^7}{5^0 + 2^0 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$5285 := \frac{5^3 + 2^{10} + 8^0 + 5^7}{5^0 + 2^0 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$5286 := \frac{5^2 + 2^{17} + 8^5 + 6^0}{5^0 + 2^4 + 8^1 + 6^1}$$

$$5286 := \frac{5^2 + 2^{17} + 8^5 + 6^0}{5^0 + 2^4 + 8^1 + 6^1}$$

$$5287 := \frac{5^0 + 2^{13} + 8^5 + 7^6}{5^1 + 2^4 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$5287 := \frac{5^0 + 2^{13} + 8^5 + 7^6}{5^1 + 2^4 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$5288 := \frac{5^7 + 2^1 + 8^0 - 8^4}{5^0 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$5289 := \frac{5^6 + 2^{20} + 8^4 + 9^2}{5^0 + 2^7 + 8^2 + 9^1}$$

$$5289 := \frac{5^6 + 2^{20} + 8^4 + 9^2}{5^0 + 2^7 + 8^2 + 9^1}$$

$$5291 := \frac{5^6 + 2^8 - 9^1 + 1^0}{-5^0 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 1^0}$$

$$5292 := \frac{5^5 + 2^7 - 9^1 + 2^{11}}{-5^0 - 2^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5293 := \frac{5^7 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 3^8}{5^1 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 3^2}$$

$$5293 := \frac{5^7 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 3^8}{5^1 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 3^2}$$

$$5294 := \frac{5^7 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 4^2}{5^0 + 2^1 + 9^1 + 4^1}$$

$$5294 := \frac{5^7 + 2^1 + 9^4 + 4^2}{5^0 + 2^1 + 9^1 + 4^1}$$

$$5295 := \frac{-5^4 - 2^4 + 9^4 - 5^4}{5^0 - 2^1 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$5295 := \frac{-5^4 - 2^4 + 9^4 - 5^4}{-5^1 + 2^1 + 9^1 - 5^1}$$

$$5296 := \frac{5^8 + 2^3 + 9^4 + 6^1}{5^0 + 2^6 + 9^1 + 6^0}$$

$$5296 := \frac{5^8 + 2^3 + 9^4 + 6^1}{5^0 + 2^6 + 9^1 + 6^0}$$

$$5297 := \frac{5^7 + 2^{15} + 9^0 + 7^3}{5^0 + 2^2 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$5297 := \frac{5^7 + 2^{15} + 9^0 + 7^3}{5^0 + 2^2 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$5298 := \frac{5^3 + 2^{19} + 9^2 + 8^1}{5^0 + 2^4 + 9^2 + 8^0}$$

$$5298 := \frac{5^3 + 2^{19} + 9^2 + 8^1}{5^0 + 2^4 + 9^2 + 8^0}$$

$$5299 := \frac{5^7 - 2^{16} - 9^3 - 9^4}{5^0 - 2^1 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$5302 := \frac{5^5 + 3^{11} + 0^1 - 2^2}{5^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 2^5}$$

$$5303 := \frac{5^5 - 3^2 + 0^1 + 3^7}{-5^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 3^0}$$

$$5304 := \frac{5^5 + 3^{11} + 0^1 + 4^3}{5^1 + 3^3 + 0^0 + 4^0}$$

$$5304 := \frac{5^5 + 3^{11} + 0^1 + 4^3}{5^1 + 3^3 + 0^0 + 4^0}$$

$$5305 := \frac{-5^5 - 3^6 - 0^0 + 5^7}{5^1 + 3^1 + 0^0 + 5^1}$$

$$5306 := \frac{5^5 + 3^7 + 0^1 - 6^1}{-5^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 6^0}$$

$$5307 := \frac{-5^6 - 3^8 + 0^1 + 7^7}{5^3 + 3^3 + 0^1 - 7^0}$$

$$5309 := \frac{5^7 + 3^{11} + 0^1 + 9^7}{5^4 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 9^2}$$

$$5309 := \frac{5^7 + 3^{11} + 0^1 + 9^7}{5^4 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 9^2}$$

$$5310 := \frac{5^5 + 3^7 - 1^0 - 0^0}{-5^0 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 0^1}$$

$$5312 := \frac{5^5 + 3^7 - 1^0 + 2^0}{-5^0 - 3^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5314 := \frac{5^5 + 3^7 + 1^0 + 4^0}{-5^0 - 3^0 - 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5319 := \frac{5^9 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 9^5}{5^4 - 3^5 - 1^0 + 9^0}$$

$$5320 := \frac{5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 0^1}{-5^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 0^1}$$

$$5321 := \frac{5^5 + 3^7 + 2^3 + 1^0}{-5^0 - 3^0 + 2^1 + 1^0}$$

$$5322 := \frac{5^7 + 3^0 + 2^5 + 2^{16}}{5^0 + 3^2 + 2^0 + 2^4}$$

$$5323 := \frac{5^7 + 3^2 + 2^{17} + 3^9}{5^0 + 3^0 + 2^5 + 3^2}$$

$$5324 := \frac{5^1 + 3^{13} + 2^{13} + 4^1}{5^2 + 3^5 + 2^5 + 4^0}$$

$$5325 := \frac{5^2 + 3^{12} + 2^{14} + 5^4}{5^0 + 3^4 + 2^4 + 5^1}$$

$$5326 := \frac{5^8 + 3^7 + 2^4 + 6^4}{5^2 + 3^2 + 2^2 + 6^2}$$

$$5327 := \frac{5^6 + 3^8 + 2^{11} + 7^4}{5^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$5328 := \frac{5^1 + 3^{11} + 2^{17} + 8^5}{5^2 + 3^3 + 2^2 + 8^1}$$

$$5329 := \frac{5^8 + 3^9 + 2^4 + 9^1}{5^0 + 3^1 + 2^6 + 9^1}$$

$$5330 := \frac{-5^2 - 3^8 + 3^{11} - 0^0}{5^0 + 3^1 + 3^3 + 0^0}$$

$$5331 := \frac{5^1 - 3^8 + 3^{11} + 1^0}{5^0 + 3^1 + 3^3 + 1^0}$$

$$5332 := \frac{5^6 - 3^3 + 3^{10} + 2^0}{5^0 + 3^1 + 3^2 + 2^0}$$

$$5333 := \frac{5^6 - 3^1 - 3^2 + 3^{10}}{5^1 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 3^1}$$

$$5334 := \frac{5^6 + 3^0 + 3^{10} + 4^0}{5^0 + 3^1 + 3^2 + 4^0}$$

$$5334 := \frac{5^6 + 3^0 + 3^{10} + 4^0}{5^0 + 3^1 + 3^2 + 4^0}$$

$$5335 := \frac{5^7 + 3^0 + 3^6 + 5^8}{5^0 + 3^0 + 3^4 + 5^1}$$

$$5335 := \frac{5^7 + 3^0 + 3^6 + 5^8}{5^0 + 3^0 + 3^4 + 5^1}$$

$$5336 := \frac{-5^7 + 3^5 + 3^{12} + 6^0}{5^2 + 3^3 + 3^3 + 6^1}$$

$$5337 := \frac{-5^6 - 3^6 + 3^{10} + 7^0}{5^0 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 7^0}$$

$$5338 := \frac{5^5 + 3^3 + 3^7 - 8^0}{5^0 + 3^0 - 3^2 + 8^1}$$

$$5339 := \frac{5^7 + 3^2 + 3^6 + 9^4}{5^0 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$5339 := \frac{5^7 + 3^2 + 3^6 + 9^4}{5^0 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$5340 := \frac{5^9 - 3^{12} + 4^6 + 0^1}{5^0 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 0^0}$$

$$5341 := \frac{5^8 - 3^{10} - 4^9 + 1^0}{5^1 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 1^1}$$

$$5342 := \frac{5^6 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 2^{14}}{5^0 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$5343 := \frac{5^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 3^{14}}{5^3 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 3^6}$$

$$5344 := \frac{5^5 + 3^{11} + 4^2 + 4^8}{5^1 + 3^2 + 4^2 + 4^2}$$

$$5345 := \frac{5^1 + 3^6 + 4^{12} + 5^1}{5^0 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5}$$

$$5345 := \frac{5^1 + 3^6 + 4^{12} + 5^1}{5^0 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5}$$

$$5346 := \frac{5^7 + 3^2 + 4^{10} + 6^4}{5^3 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 6^0}$$

$$5346 := \frac{5^7 + 3^2 + 4^{10} + 6^4}{5^3 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 6^0}$$

$$5347 := \frac{5^8 + 3^{12} + 4^{10} + 7^4}{5^0 + 3^2 + 4^2 + 7^3}$$

$$5347 := \frac{5^8 + 3^{12} + 4^{10} + 7^4}{5^0 + 3^2 + 4^2 + 7^3}$$

$$5348 := \frac{5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5}{5^1 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$5348 := \frac{5^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 8^5}{5^1 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$5349 := \frac{5^6 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 9^3}{-5^0 - 3^0 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5350 := \frac{-5^4 + 3^{10} - 5^6 + 0^0}{5^0 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 0^0}$$

$$5351 := \frac{5^8 - 3^1 + 5^8 - 1^0}{-5^1 + 3^3 + 5^3 - 1^0}$$

$$5352 := \frac{-5^6 - 3^9 + 5^7 - 2^0}{5^0 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 2^0}$$

$$5353 := \frac{5^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 3^{10}}{5^0 + 3^1 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$5353 := \frac{5^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 3^{10}}{5^0 + 3^1 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$5354 := \frac{-5^0 + 3^7 + 5^7 - 4^0}{5^0 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5355 := \frac{5^0 + 3^6 + 5^6 + 5^8}{5^2 + 3^0 + 5^2 + 5^2}$$

$$5355 := \frac{5^0 + 3^6 + 5^6 + 5^8}{5^2 + 3^0 + 5^2 + 5^2}$$

$$5356 := \frac{-5^6 - 3^4 + 5^8 + 6^0}{-5^1 + 3^4 - 5^1 - 6^0}$$

$$5357 := \frac{-5^3 + 3^{11} + 5^6 - 7^6}{5^0 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 7^1}$$

$$5358 := \frac{-5^4 - 3^7 + 5^9 - 8^0}{-5^1 + 3^5 + 5^3 + 8^0}$$

$$5359 := \frac{-5^5 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 9^0}{5^0 + 3^1 + 5^0 + 9^1}$$

$$5360 := \frac{-5^3 + 3^{10} + 6^2 + 0^1}{5^0 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 0^0}$$

$$5361 := \frac{5^6 + 3^5 + 6^3 - 1^0}{-5^0 - 3^0 + 6^1 - 1^0}$$

$$5362 := \frac{5^7 + 3^0 + 6^7 + 2^{16}}{5^1 + 3^2 + 6^0 + 2^6}$$

$$5362 := \frac{5^7 + 3^0 + 6^7 + 2^{16}}{5^1 + 3^2 + 6^0 + 2^6}$$

$$5363 := \frac{5^3 - 3^3 - 6^4 + 3^8}{-5^0 - 3^0 + 6^1 - 3^1}$$

$$5364 := \frac{5^3 + 3^7 + 6^6 + 4^9}{5^1 + 3^0 + 6^2 + 4^2}$$

$$5365 := \frac{-5^2 + 3^8 - 6^4 + 5^3}{5^0 + 3^0 - 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$5366 := \frac{5^5 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 6^4}{-5^0 - 3^1 - 6^0 + 6^1}$$

$$5367 := \frac{5^9 + 3^{11} + 6^7 + 7^6}{5^1 + 3^5 + 6^3 + 7^1}$$

$$5368 := \frac{5^1 + 3^{11} + 6^8 + 8^5}{5^3 + 3^1 + 6^3 + 8^1}$$

$$5368 := \frac{5^1 + 3^{11} + 6^8 + 8^5}{5^3 + 3^1 + 6^3 + 8^1}$$

$$5369 := \frac{5^0 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 9^5}{5^0 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5369 := \frac{5^0 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 9^5}{5^0 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5370 := \frac{-5^5 + 3^8 + 7^7 + 0^0}{5^3 + 3^3 + 7^0 + 0^0}$$

$$5371 := \frac{5^3 + 3^{16} + 7^8 + 1^0}{5^3 + 3^8 + 7^4 + 1^0}$$

$$5371 := \frac{5^3 + 3^{16} + 7^8 + 1^0}{5^3 + 3^8 + 7^4 + 1^0}$$

$$5372 := \frac{5^4 + 3^0 + 7^{10} + 2^0}{5^3 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 2^{15}}$$

$$5372 := \frac{5^4 + 3^0 + 7^{10} + 2^0}{5^3 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 2^{15}}$$

$$5373 := \frac{5^5 + 3^2 + 7^4 + 3^{11}}{5^1 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 3^3}$$

$$5373 := \frac{5^5 + 3^2 + 7^4 + 3^{11}}{5^1 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 3^3}$$

$$5374 := \frac{-5^6 + 3^4 + 7^6 + 4^0}{5^1 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 4^1}$$

$$5375 := \frac{5^0 + 3^{12} + 7^5 + 5^0}{5^0 + 3^3 + 7^2 + 5^2}$$

$$5375 := \frac{5^0 + 3^{12} + 7^5 + 5^0}{5^0 + 3^3 + 7^2 + 5^2}$$

$$5376 := \frac{5^4 - 3^0 + 7^6 - 6^0}{5^1 + 3^2 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$5377 := \frac{-5^4 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 7^4}{5^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5378 := \frac{5^6 + 3^8 - 7^5 - 8^0}{-5^0 + 3^0 - 7^1 + 8^1}$$

$$5379 := \frac{5^5 + 3^6 + 7^3 + 9^4}{-5^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$5380 := \frac{5^6 + 3^1 + 8^3 + 0^1}{5^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$5380 := \frac{5^6 + 3^1 + 8^3 + 0^1}{5^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$5381 := \frac{5^5 + 3^9 + 8^4 + 1^0}{-5^0 - 3^0 + 8^1 - 1^0}$$

$$5382 := \frac{5^2 + 3^{10} + 8^2 + 2^6}{5^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 2^3}$$

$$5382 := \frac{5^2 + 3^{10} + 8^2 + 2^6}{5^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 2^3}$$

$$5383 := \frac{5^{10} + 3^1 + 8^8 + 3^6}{5^2 + 3^4 + 8^4 + 3^6}$$

$$5383 := \frac{5^{10} + 3^1 + 8^8 + 3^6}{5^2 + 3^4 + 8^4 + 3^6}$$

$$5384 := \frac{5^1 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 4^{14}}{5^4 + 3^4 + 8^5 + 4^7}$$

$$5385 := \frac{5^1 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 5^7}{5^1 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$5385 := \frac{5^1 + 3^7 + 8^5 + 5^7}{5^1 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$5386 := \frac{5^3 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 6^7}{5^1 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 6^2}$$

$$5386 := \frac{5^3 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 6^7}{5^1 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 6^2}$$

$$5387 := \frac{5^6 + 3^{10} + 8^7 + 7^6}{5^3 + 3^5 + 8^1 + 7^2}$$

$$5387 := \frac{5^6 + 3^{10} + 8^7 + 7^6}{5^3 + 3^5 + 8^1 + 7^2}$$

$$5388 := \frac{5^1 + 3^{13} + 8^1 + 8^3}{5^0 - 3^6 + 8^3 + 8^3}$$

$$5389 := \frac{5^6 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 9^2}{-5^0 + 3^0 + 8^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5390 := \frac{-5^0 + 3^5 + 9^5 - 0^0}{5^0 + 3^0 + 9^1 + 0^1}$$

$$5391 := \frac{-5^5 + 3^0 + 9^6 + 1^0}{5^2 - 3^2 + 9^2 + 1^0}$$

$$5392 := \frac{5^5 + 3^7 + 9^2 - 2^0}{-5^0 - 3^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5393 := \frac{5^1 + 3^7 - 9^5 + 3^{12}}{5^0 + 3^1 + 9^2 + 3^1}$$

$$5394 := \frac{5^3 + 3^{11} + 9^3 + 4^0}{5^0 + 3^3 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5395 := \frac{5^0 + 3^{13} + 9^6 - 5^9}{5^1 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 5^2}$$

$$5396 := \frac{5^9 - 3^4 - 9^5 + 6^0}{5^3 + 3^0 + 9^1 + 6^3}$$

$$5397 := \frac{5^3 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 7^5}{5^1 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5397 := \frac{5^3 + 3^9 + 9^4 + 7^5}{5^1 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5399 := \frac{5^8 + 3^0 + 9^4 + 9^6}{5^0 + 3^2 + 9^2 + 9^2}$$

$$5399 := \frac{5^8 + 3^0 + 9^4 + 9^6}{5^0 + 3^2 + 9^2 + 9^2}$$

$$5402 := \frac{5^8 - 4^4 - 0^0 - 2^{17}}{-5^0 + 4^2 + 0^0 + 2^5}$$

$$5404 := \frac{-5^4 - 4^3 + 0^0 + 4^8}{-5^0 - 4^1 + 0^0 + 4^2}$$

$$5405 := \frac{-5^0 + 4^{10} + 0^1 - 5^1}{5^1 + 4^3 + 0^1 + 5^3}$$

$$5406 := \frac{5^8 + 4^4 + 0^0 + 6^8}{5^3 + 4^4 + 0^0 + 6^0}$$

$$5406 := \frac{5^8 + 4^4 + 0^0 + 6^8}{5^3 + 4^4 + 0^0 + 6^0}$$

$$5407 := \frac{-5^1 - 4^6 - 0^0 + 7^6}{-5^0 + 4^2 - 0^0 + 7^1}$$

$$5408 := \frac{5^8 - 4^6 - 0^0 - 8^6}{5^1 + 4^2 + 0^0 + 8^0}$$

$$5409 := \frac{-5^8 + 4^{11} + 0^1 - 9^4}{-5^2 - 4^0 - 0^0 + 9^3}$$

$$5412 := \frac{-5^4 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 2^5}{5^1 + 4^1 + 1^1 + 2^1}$$

$$5413 := \frac{-5^3 - 4^5 + 1^0 + 3^8}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 1^0 - 3^0}$$

$$5414 := \frac{-5^3 - 4^2 - 1^0 + 4^7}{-5^0 - 4^0 + 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5415 := \frac{5^4 - 4^1 - 1^0 + 5^6}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$5416 := \frac{5^2 + 4^6 - 1^0 + 6^4}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 1^0 - 6^0}$$

$$5417 := \frac{-5^3 + 4^7 - 1^0 - 7^1}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 1^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5418 := \frac{-5^1 - 4^4 + 1^0 + 8^5}{5^0 - 4^1 + 1^0 + 8^1}$$

$$5419 := \frac{-5^3 + 4^7 - 1^0 - 9^0}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 1^0 + 9^0}$$

$$5420 := \frac{5^1 + 4^7 - 2^7 - 0^0}{5^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 0^1}$$

$$5421 := \frac{5^9 + 4^8 - 2^{11} - 1^0}{-5^3 - 4^2 + 2^9 + 1^0}$$

$$5422 := \frac{5^6 + 4^0 + 2^7 + 2^9}{-5^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5423 := \frac{5^0 + 4^1 + 2^3 + 3^{12}}{5^0 + 4^3 + 2^5 + 3^0}$$

$$5423 := \frac{5^0 + 4^1 + 2^3 + 3^{12}}{5^0 + 4^3 + 2^5 + 3^0}$$

$$5424 := \frac{-5^4 + 4^0 + 2^9 + 4^7}{-5^0 - 4^0 + 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5425 := \frac{5^5 + 4^2 + 2^{14} + 5^7}{5^0 + 4^1 + 2^3 + 5^1}$$

$$5425 := \frac{5^5 + 4^2 + 2^{14} + 5^7}{5^0 + 4^1 + 2^3 + 5^1}$$

$$5426 := \frac{5^7 + 4^0 + 2^4 + 6^6}{5^1 + 4^0 + 2^4 + 6^0}$$

$$5426 := \frac{5^7 + 4^0 + 2^4 + 6^6}{5^1 + 4^0 + 2^4 + 6^0}$$

$$5427 := \frac{5^5 + 4^9 + 2^7 + 7^5}{5^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 7^2}$$

$$5427 := \frac{5^5 + 4^9 + 2^7 + 7^5}{5^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 7^2}$$

$$5428 := \frac{5^5 + 4^4 + 2^{11} - 8^0}{-5^0 - 4^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$5429 := \frac{5^2 + 4^3 + 2^9 + 9^6}{5^0 + 4^3 + 2^5 + 9^0}$$

$$5429 := \frac{5^2 + 4^3 + 2^9 + 9^6}{5^0 + 4^3 + 2^5 + 9^0}$$

$$5430 := \frac{5^6 - 4^3 + 3^6 + 0^1}{5^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$$

$$5431 := \frac{5^7 - 4^2 + 3^{11} + 1^0}{5^1 + 4^2 + 3^3 - 1^0}$$

$$5432 := \frac{5^5 + 4^7 + 3^7 + 2^5}{5^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$5432 := \frac{5^5 + 4^7 + 3^7 + 2^5}{5^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$5432 := \frac{5^6 - 4^6 - 3^6 + 2^6}{5^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 - 2^0}$$

$$5433 := \frac{5^4 - 4^5 - 3^6 + 3^8}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 3^0 - 3^0}$$

$$5434 := \frac{5^1 + 4^5 + 3^9 + 4^5}{5^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$5434 := \frac{5^1 + 4^5 + 3^9 + 4^5}{5^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$5435 := \frac{5^0 + 4^7 - 3^4 + 5^0}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$5436 := \frac{5^1 + 4^7 + 3^7 + 6^6}{5^0 + 4^0 + 3^2 + 6^0}$$

$$5436 := \frac{5^1 + 4^7 + 3^7 + 6^6}{5^0 + 4^0 + 3^2 + 6^0}$$

$$5437 := \frac{5^2 + 4^{13} + 3^0 + 7^0}{5^5 + 4^4 + 3^8 + 7^4}$$

$$5437 := \frac{5^2 + 4^{13} + 3^0 + 7^0}{5^5 + 4^4 + 3^8 + 7^4}$$

$$5438 := \frac{5^0 + 4^4 + 3^{10} + 8^3}{5^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 8^1}$$

$$5438 := \frac{5^0 + 4^4 + 3^{10} + 8^3}{5^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 8^1}$$

$$5439 := \frac{-5^3 - 4^5 + 3^3 + 9^4}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 3^0 - 9^0}$$

$$5440 := \frac{-5^0 - 4^3 + 4^7 + 0^0}{5^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$$

$$5441 := \frac{-5^7 + 4^9 + 4^9 - 1^0}{5^0 + 4^2 + 4^3 + 1^0}$$

$$5442 := \frac{5^1 + 4^0 - 4^3 + 2^{14}}{-5^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5443 := \frac{5^8 + 4^1 + 4^5 + 3^5}{5^0 + 4^1 + 4^3 + 3^1}$$

$$5443 := \frac{5^8 + 4^1 + 4^5 + 3^5}{5^0 + 4^1 + 4^3 + 3^1}$$

$$5444 := \frac{-5^4 + 4^0 - 4^8 + 4^9}{5^1 - 4^0 + 4^2 + 4^2}$$

$$5445 := \frac{-5^2 + 4^0 + 4^7 - 5^2}{-5^0 - 4^0 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$5446 := \frac{5^5 + 4^0 + 4^5 + 6^4}{-5^0 - 4^0 + 4^1 - 6^0}$$

$$5447 := \frac{5^7 - 4^6 - 4^8 + 7^4}{-5^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5448 := \frac{5^2 - 4^0 + 4^7 - 8^2}{-5^0 - 4^0 + 4^1 + 8^0}$$

$$5449 := \frac{5^4 - 4^0 + 4^6 + 9^3}{-5^0 - 4^0 + 4^1 - 9^0}$$

$$5451 := \frac{-5^1 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 1^0}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$5452 := \frac{5^3 + 4^{10} + 5^8 + 2^1}{5^0 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 2^1}$$

$$5452 := \frac{5^3 + 4^{10} + 5^8 + 2^1}{5^0 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 2^1}$$

$$5453 := \frac{5^4 + 4^8 + 5^6 + 3^2}{5^0 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$5454 := \frac{-5^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 4^6}{-5^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$5455 := \frac{5^0 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 5^2}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$5456 := \frac{-5^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^5}{-5^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$5457 := \frac{5^3 + 4^7 + 5^9 + 7^3}{5^0 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 7^3}$$

$$5457 := \frac{5^3 + 4^7 + 5^9 + 7^3}{5^0 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 7^3}$$

$$5458 := \frac{-5^0 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 8^1}{-5^0 + 4^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$5459 := \frac{5^0 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 9^1}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$5460 := \frac{5^0 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 0^0}{5^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 0^1}$	$5470 := \frac{5^2 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 0^1}{5^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 0^1}$	$5483 := \frac{5^3 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 3^0}{5^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 3^1}$
$5461 := \frac{-5^0 + 4^7 - 6^0 + 1^0}{-5^0 - 4^0 + 6^1 - 1^0}$	$5471 := \frac{5^9 + 4^2 + 7^1 - 1^0}{-5^0 + 4^2 + 7^3 - 1^0}$	$5483 := \frac{5^3 + 4^1 + 8^5 + 3^0}{5^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 3^1}$
$5462 := \frac{5^1 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 2^{15}}{5^0 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 2^0}$	$5472 := \frac{5^3 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 2^1}{5^1 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 2^1}$	$5484 := \frac{5^1 - 4^0 + 8^2 + 4^7}{-5^0 - 4^0 + 8^0 + 4^1}$
$5462 := \frac{5^1 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 2^{15}}{5^0 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 2^0}$	$5472 := \frac{5^3 + 4^8 + 7^0 + 2^1}{5^1 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 2^1}$	$5485 := \frac{5^5 + 4^5 + 8^0 + 5^7}{5^0 + 4^0 + 8^1 + 5^1}$
$5463 := \frac{5^1 + 4^8 + 6^1 + 3^2}{5^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 3^2}$	$5473 := \frac{5^5 + 4^{10} + 7^4 + 3^7}{5^3 + 4^2 + 7^2 + 3^1}$	$5485 := \frac{5^5 + 4^5 + 8^0 + 5^7}{5^0 + 4^0 + 8^1 + 5^1}$
$5463 := \frac{5^1 + 4^8 + 6^1 + 3^2}{5^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 3^2}$	$5473 := \frac{5^5 + 4^{10} + 7^4 + 3^7}{5^3 + 4^2 + 7^2 + 3^1}$	$5486 := \frac{-5^9 + 4^6 + 8^7 - 6^0}{-5^0 - 4^2 + 8^1 + 6^2}$
$5464 := \frac{5^2 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 4^8}{5^0 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 4^1}$	$5474 := \frac{5^8 + 4^6 + 7^0 + 4^{12}}{5^5 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 4^1}$	$5487 := \frac{5^5 + 4^6 + 8^4 - 7^3}{-5^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$
$5464 := \frac{5^2 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 4^8}{5^0 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 4^1}$	$5474 := \frac{5^8 + 4^6 + 7^0 + 4^{12}}{5^5 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 4^1}$	$5488 := \frac{5^4 - 4^5 - 8^0 + 8^8}{5^5 + 4^1 - 8^1 - 8^2}$
$5465 := \frac{5^5 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 5^9}{5^0 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 5^3}$	$5475 := \frac{-5^0 - 4^4 + 7^5 - 5^3}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 7^0 + 5^0}$	$5489 := \frac{5^0 + 4^7 + 8^0 + 9^2}{5^0 + 4^0 - 8^1 + 9^1}$
$5465 := \frac{5^5 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 5^9}{5^0 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 5^3}$	$5476 := \frac{-5^5 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 6^5}{5^0 + 4^0 - 7^1 + 6^1}$	$5490 := \frac{5^1 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 0^1}{5^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 0^1}$
$5466 := \frac{5^7 + 4^0 + 6^5 + 6^8}{5^2 + 4^4 + 6^1 + 6^2}$	$5477 := \frac{-5^0 + 4^7 - 7^0 + 7^2}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 7^0 + 7^0}$	$5490 := \frac{5^1 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 0^1}{5^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 0^1}$
$5466 := \frac{5^7 + 4^0 + 6^5 + 6^8}{5^2 + 4^4 + 6^1 + 6^2}$	$5478 := \frac{5^7 + 4^6 + 7^2 + 8^5}{5^1 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 8^1}$	$5490 := \frac{-5^5 - 4^5 + 9^5 - 0^5}{5^1 - 4^1 + 9^1 - 0^1}$
$5467 := \frac{5^2 + 4^8 + 6^2 + 7^1}{5^0 + 4^1 + 6^1 + 7^0}$	$5478 := \frac{5^7 + 4^6 + 7^2 + 8^5}{5^1 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 8^1}$	$5491 := \frac{5^7 - 4^3 + 9^6 - 1^0}{5^2 + 4^1 + 9^2 + 1^0}$
$5467 := \frac{5^2 + 4^8 + 6^2 + 7^1}{5^0 + 4^1 + 6^1 + 7^0}$	$5479 := \frac{5^1 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 9^6}{5^1 + 4^1 + 7^1 + 9^2}$	$5492 := \frac{-5^1 + 4^2 + 9^2 + 2^{14}}{-5^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$
$5468 := \frac{5^2 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 8^0}{-5^0 - 4^0 + 6^1 - 8^0}$	$5479 := \frac{5^1 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 9^6}{5^1 + 4^1 + 7^1 + 9^2}$	$5493 := \frac{5^2 + 4^6 + 9^0 + 3^{11}}{5^0 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 3^3}$
$5469 := \frac{5^1 + 4^8 + 6^1 + 9^2}{5^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 9^1}$	$5481 := \frac{5^9 + 4^9 + 8^6 - 1^0}{5^1 - 4^3 + 8^3 - 1^0}$	$5493 := \frac{5^2 + 4^6 + 9^0 + 3^{11}}{5^0 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 3^3}$
$5469 := \frac{5^1 + 4^8 + 6^1 + 9^2}{5^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 9^1}$	$5482 := \frac{5^7 + 4^0 + 8^1 + 2^{12}}{5^0 + 4^1 + 8^1 + 2^1}$	$5494 := \frac{5^8 + 4^5 + 9^6 + 4^7}{5^2 + 4^0 + 9^2 + 4^3}$
$5470 := \frac{5^2 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 0^1}{5^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 0^1}$	$5482 := \frac{5^7 + 4^0 + 8^1 + 2^{12}}{5^0 + 4^1 + 8^1 + 2^1}$	$5494 := \frac{5^8 + 4^5 + 9^6 + 4^7}{5^2 + 4^0 + 9^2 + 4^3}$

$$5495 := \frac{-5^1 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 5^2}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$5496 := \frac{-5^1 - 4^5 + 9^4 - 6^2}{-5^0 - 4^0 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$5497 := \frac{5^2 + 4^7 + 9^2 + 7^0}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5498 := \frac{5^2 - 4^5 + 9^4 - 8^2}{5^0 + 4^0 - 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$5499 := \frac{-5^4 + 4^7 + 9^1 + 9^3}{-5^0 + 4^1 - 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$5502 := \frac{5^4 + 5^6 + 0^1 + 2^8}{5^0 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 2^0}$$

$$5502 := \frac{5^4 + 5^6 + 0^1 + 2^8}{5^0 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 2^0}$$

$$5503 := \frac{-5^2 + 5^7 + 0^1 - 3^8}{5^1 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 3^1}$$

$$5507 := \frac{5^3 - 5^5 + 0^1 + 7^7}{5^2 + 5^3 + 0^1 - 7^0}$$

$$5521 := \frac{-5^4 + 5^7 + 2^{19} + 1^0}{-5^0 + 5^3 - 2^4 + 1^0}$$

$$5522 := \frac{5^5 + 5^5 + 2^{15} + 2^{15}}{5^1 + 5^1 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5522 := \frac{5^5 + 5^5 + 2^{15} + 2^{15}}{5^1 + 5^1 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5523 := \frac{5^5 + 5^{11} + 2^1 + 3^9}{5^0 + 5^4 + 2^{13} + 3^3}$$

$$5523 := \frac{5^5 + 5^{11} + 2^1 + 3^9}{5^0 + 5^4 + 2^{13} + 3^3}$$

$$5524 := \frac{5^3 + 5^4 + 2^1 + 4^8}{5^0 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$5524 := \frac{5^3 + 5^4 + 2^1 + 4^8}{5^0 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$5525 := \frac{5^0 + 5^4 + 2^{10} + 5^8}{5^0 + 5^0 + 2^6 + 5^1}$$

$$5525 := \frac{5^0 + 5^4 + 2^{10} + 5^8}{5^0 + 5^0 + 2^6 + 5^1}$$

$$5526 := \frac{5^8 + 5^8 + 2^{14} + 6^7}{5^1 + 5^3 + 2^6 + 6^0}$$

$$5526 := \frac{5^8 + 5^8 + 2^{14} + 6^7}{5^1 + 5^3 + 2^6 + 6^0}$$

$$5527 := \frac{-5^0 + 5^5 + 2^1 + 7^4}{-5^0 - 5^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$5528 := \frac{-5^0 + 5^6 + 2^{10} - 8^2}{-5^0 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$5529 := \frac{5^5 + 5^5 + 2^3 - 9^3}{-5^0 - 5^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5530 := \frac{-5^4 - 5^5 + 3^{10} + 0^0}{5^0 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 0^0}$$

$$5531 := \frac{5^8 + 5^9 + 3^{13} - 1^0}{5^1 + 5^4 + 3^4 + 1^0}$$

$$5532 := \frac{5^0 - 5^3 + 3^{11} + 2^0}{5^1 + 5^2 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$5533 := \frac{-5^1 - 5^1 - 3^4 + 3^{11}}{5^0 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 3^3}$$

$$5534 := \frac{-5^9 - 5^9 + 3^{15} + 4^0}{-5^1 + 5^4 + 3^5 + 4^5}$$

$$5535 := \frac{-5^0 - 5^4 - 3^2 + 5^7}{5^0 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 5^1}$$

$$5536 := \frac{-5^4 + 5^7 + 3^1 + 6^0}{5^1 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 6^0}$$

$$5537 := \frac{5^1 + 5^2 + 3^{11} + 7^1}{5^1 + 5^2 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5537 := \frac{5^1 + 5^2 + 3^{11} + 7^1}{5^1 + 5^2 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5538 := \frac{5^2 + 5^2 + 3^{15} + 8^0}{5^0 + 5^3 + 3^8 - 8^4}$$

$$5539 := \frac{-5^1 + 5^2 + 3^{11} + 9^2}{5^1 + 5^2 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$5541 := \frac{-5^2 + 5^6 + 4^5 - 1^0}{-5^0 - 5^0 + 4^1 + 1^0}$$

$$5542 := \frac{5^4 + 5^5 - 4^4 + 2^{11}}{-5^0 - 5^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5543 := \frac{5^0 + 5^1 - 4^5 + 3^8}{-5^0 - 5^0 + 4^1 - 3^0}$$

$$5544 := \frac{-5^0 + 5^6 - 4^2 + 4^5}{-5^0 - 5^0 + 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5545 := \frac{5^0 + 5^3 + 4^7 + 5^3}{-5^0 - 5^0 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$5546 := \frac{5^7 + 5^9 + 4^6 + 6^2}{5^2 + 5^3 + 4^0 + 6^3}$$

$$5546 := \frac{5^7 + 5^9 + 4^6 + 6^2}{5^2 + 5^3 + 4^0 + 6^3}$$

$$5547 := \frac{5^1 + 5^5 + 4^2 + 7^4}{-5^0 - 5^0 + 4^1 - 7^0}$$

$$5548 := \frac{-5^1 + 5^7 + 4^3 - 8^3}{5^0 + 5^0 + 4^1 + 8^1}$$

$$5549 := \frac{-5^0 + 5^6 + 4^5 - 9^0}{-5^0 - 5^0 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5551 := \frac{5^6 + 5^6 + 5^8 + 1^0}{5^2 + 5^2 + 5^2 + 1^2}$$

$$5551 := \frac{5^6 + 5^6 + 5^8 + 1^0}{5^2 + 5^2 + 5^2 + 1^2}$$

$$5553 := \frac{5^0 + 5^2 + 5^6 + 3^8}{5^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$5553 := \frac{5^0 + 5^2 + 5^6 + 3^8}{5^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$5558 := \frac{-5^4 + 5^7 + 5^7 - 8^0}{5^0 + 5^0 + 5^2 + 8^0}$$

$$5559 := \frac{5^2 + 5^2 + 5^6 + 9^4}{5^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$5559 := \frac{5^2 + 5^2 + 5^6 + 9^4}{5^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$5562 := \frac{5^4 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 2^{12}}{-5^0 - 5^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5563 := \frac{5^4 + 5^5 + 6^7 + 3^3}{5^0 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 3^2}$$

$$5563 := \frac{5^4 + 5^5 + 6^7 + 3^3}{5^0 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 3^2}$$

$$5564 := \frac{-5^1 - 5^4 - 6^1 + 4^9}{5^1 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 4^0}$$

$$5565 := \frac{-5^0 - 5^2 + 6^3 + 5^9}{5^1 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 5^3}$$

$$5566 := \frac{5^4 + 5^8 + 6^1 - 6^7}{-5^1 - 5^1 - 6^1 + 6^2}$$

$$5567 := \frac{5^5 + 5^{10} + 6^{11} + 7^{10}}{5^1 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 7^6}$$

$$5568 := \frac{5^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^6}{5^0 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 8^1}$$

$$5568 := \frac{5^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^6}{5^0 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 8^1}$$

$$5569 := \frac{-5^1 - 5^7 + 6^8 + 9^6}{-5^1 - 5^3 - 6^3 + 9^3}$$

$$5570 := \frac{-5^5 - 5^5 + 7^6 + 0^0}{5^0 + 5^2 - 7^1 + 0^0}$$

$$5571 := \frac{-5^3 + 5^7 - 7^1 + 1^0}{5^0 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 1^0}$$

$$5572 := \frac{-5^2 + 5^7 - 7^5 - 2^0}{5^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 2^3}$$

$$5573 := \frac{5^6 + 5^6 + 7^0 + 3^7}{5^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 3^1}$$

$$5573 := \frac{5^6 + 5^6 + 7^0 + 3^7}{5^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 3^1}$$

$$5574 := \frac{-5^1 + 5^7 - 7^5 + 4^0}{5^0 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5575 := \frac{-5^0 - 5^2 - 7^2 + 5^7}{5^0 + 5^0 + 7^1 + 5^1}$$

$$5576 := \frac{5^3 + 5^{11} - 7^8 - 6^0}{5^0 - 5^1 - 7^2 + 6^5}$$

$$5577 := \frac{-5^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 + 7^5}{5^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5578 := \frac{-5^2 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 8^0}{5^0 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 8^0}$$

$$5579 := \frac{-5^2 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^0}{5^0 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5580 := \frac{-5^1 + 5^7 - 8^0 + 0^0}{5^0 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 0^1}$$

$$5582 := \frac{5^7 + 5^7 + 8^6 + 2^8}{5^1 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 2^6}$$

$$5582 := \frac{5^7 + 5^7 + 8^6 + 2^8}{5^1 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 2^6}$$

$$5583 := \frac{-5^3 + 5^4 + 8^6 - 3^5}{5^1 + 5^2 + 8^1 + 3^2}$$

$$5584 := \frac{-5^1 + 5^7 - 8^1 + 4^3}{5^0 + 5^0 + 8^1 + 4^1}$$

$$5585 := \frac{-5^0 - 5^2 - 8^6 + 5^8}{5^1 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$5586 := \frac{5^0 - 5^3 - 8^3 + 6^7}{5^0 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 6^2}$$

$$5587 := \frac{5^7 + 5^8 + 8^3 + 7^5}{5^1 + 5^2 + 8^1 + 7^2}$$

$$5587 := \frac{5^7 + 5^8 + 8^3 + 7^5}{5^1 + 5^2 + 8^1 + 7^2}$$

$$5588 := \frac{-5^7 + 5^8 - 8^2 - 8^6}{-5^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$5589 := \frac{5^4 + 5^4 + 8^4 + 9^8}{5^1 + 5^4 + 8^3 + 9^4}$$

$$5589 := \frac{5^4 + 5^4 + 8^4 + 9^8}{5^1 + 5^4 + 8^3 + 9^4}$$

$$5590 := \frac{-5^2 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 0^0}{-5^0 + 5^0 + 9^1 + 0^0}$$

$$5592 := \frac{-5^1 - 5^5 + 9^5 + 2^0}{-5^0 + 5^0 + 9^1 + 2^0}$$

$$5593 := \frac{5^1 - 5^5 + 9^0 + 3^{10}}{5^0 + 5^1 + 9^0 + 3^1}$$

$$5594 := \frac{-5^6 + 5^7 - 9^4 + 4^0}{-5^0 + 5^0 + 9^1 + 4^0}$$

$$5595 := \frac{5^0 + 5^2 + 9^5 - 5^5}{-5^0 + 5^0 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$5597 := \frac{-5^5 + 5^8 - 9^4 - 7^3}{5^1 + 5^1 + 9^1 + 7^2}$$

$$5602 := \frac{5^3 + 6^5 + 0^0 + 2^{19}}{5^2 + 6^1 + 0^1 + 2^6}$$

$$5602 := \frac{5^3 + 6^5 + 0^0 + 2^{19}}{5^2 + 6^1 + 0^1 + 2^6}$$

$$5603 := \frac{-5^7 + 6^6 + 0^1 + 3^{11}}{-5^0 - 6^0 + 0^0 + 3^3}$$

$$5605 := \frac{-5^4 + 6^6 - 0^0 + 5^6}{5^1 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 5^1}$$

$$5606 := \frac{-5^7 + 6^1 - 0^0 + 6^7}{-5^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 6^2}$$

$$5613 := \frac{5^2 + 6^5 - 1^0 - 3^7}{-5^0 + 6^1 - 1^0 - 3^1}$$

$$5614 := \frac{5^7 + 6^3 - 1^0 + 4^4}{5^1 + 6^1 - 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5618 := \frac{5^2 + 6^7 - 1^0 - 8^5}{-5^0 + 6^2 + 1^0 + 8^1}$$

$$5619 := \frac{5^{12} + 6^2 - 1^0 - 9^3}{-5^5 + 6^6 - 1^0 - 9^2}$$

$$5621 := \frac{5^9 + 6^7 + 2^{12} + 1^0}{5^3 + 6^4 - 2^{10} + 1^0}$$

$$5622 := \frac{5^6 + 6^3 + 2^0 + 2^{10}}{-5^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5623 := \frac{5^2 + 6^3 + 2^{15} + 3^6}{5^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 3^1}$$

$$5623 := \frac{5^2 + 6^3 + 2^{15} + 3^6}{5^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 3^1}$$

$$5624 := \frac{-5^4 + 6^5 + 2^0 + 4^6}{-5^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$5625 := \frac{5^4 + 6^7 + 2^6 + 5^4}{5^0 + 6^2 + 2^3 + 5^1}$$

$$5625 := \frac{5^4 + 6^7 + 2^6 + 5^4}{5^0 + 6^2 + 2^3 + 5^1}$$

$$5626 := \frac{-5^4 + 6^0 - 2^{10} + 6^6}{5^1 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$5627 := \frac{5^1 + 6^6 + 2^{16} + 7^3}{5^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 7^1}$$

$$5627 := \frac{5^1 + 6^6 + 2^{16} + 7^3}{5^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 7^1}$$

$$5628 := \frac{-5^2 + 6^0 + 2^{10} + 8^5}{-5^0 + 6^0 - 2^1 + 8^1}$$

$$5629 := \frac{5^6 + 6^2 + 2^{12} + 9^5}{5^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5629 := \frac{5^6 + 6^2 + 2^{12} + 9^5}{5^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5630 := \frac{-5^6 + 6^6 + 3^{10} + 0^1}{5^0 + 6^1 + 3^2 + 0^1}$$

$$5631 := \frac{5^6 + 6^4 - 3^3 - 1^0}{-5^0 + 6^1 - 3^0 - 1^0}$$

$$5632 := \frac{5^7 + 6^3 + 3^{11} + 2^{16}}{5^2 + 6^0 + 3^3 + 2^2}$$

$$5632 := \frac{5^7 + 6^3 + 3^{11} + 2^{16}}{5^2 + 6^0 + 3^3 + 2^2}$$

$$5633 := \frac{5^3 - 6^4 + 3^5 + 3^8}{-5^0 + 6^1 - 3^0 - 3^1}$$

$$5634 := \frac{5^7 + 6^1 + 3^6 + 4^2}{5^0 + 6^1 + 3^1 + 4^1}$$

$$5634 := \frac{5^7 + 6^1 + 3^6 + 4^2}{5^0 + 6^1 + 3^1 + 4^1}$$

$$5635 := \frac{5^0 + 6^7 + 3^1 + 5^8}{5^0 + 6^2 + 3^4 + 5^0}$$

$$5635 := \frac{5^0 + 6^7 + 3^1 + 5^8}{5^0 + 6^2 + 3^4 + 5^0}$$

$$5636 := \frac{5^5 + 6^4 - 3^4 + 6^4}{-5^0 - 6^0 - 3^1 + 6^1}$$

$$5637 := \frac{5^5 + 6^3 + 3^{11} + 7^5}{5^0 + 6^1 + 3^3 + 7^0}$$

$$5637 := \frac{5^5 + 6^3 + 3^{11} + 7^5}{5^0 + 6^1 + 3^3 + 7^0}$$

$$5638 := \frac{5^4 - 6^1 + 3^8 + 8^4}{-5^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$5639 := \frac{5^{11} + 6^1 + 3^{12} + 9^8}{5^6 + 6^1 + 3^3 + 9^3}$$

$$5639 := \frac{5^{11} + 6^1 + 3^{12} + 9^8}{5^6 + 6^1 + 3^3 + 9^3}$$

$$5640 := \frac{5^6 + 6^4 - 4^0 + 0^1}{5^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$$

$$5641 := \frac{5^6 + 6^4 + 4^0 + 1^0}{-5^0 - 6^0 + 4^1 + 1^0}$$

$$5642 := \frac{5^2 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 2^{12}}{5^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$5642 := \frac{5^2 + 6^6 + 4^0 + 2^{12}}{5^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$5643 := \frac{5^1 + 6^7 + 4^7 + 3^9}{5^0 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 3^1}$$

$$5643 := \frac{5^1 + 6^7 + 4^7 + 3^9}{5^0 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 3^1}$$

$$5644 := \frac{5^8 - 6^7 - 4^0 - 4^8}{5^1 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$5645 := \frac{5^1 + 6^2 + 4^1 + 5^9}{5^0 + 6^3 + 4^1 + 5^3}$$

$$5645 := \frac{5^1 + 6^2 + 4^1 + 5^9}{5^0 + 6^3 + 4^1 + 5^3}$$

$$5646 := \frac{5^7 + 6^7 + 4^0 + 6^7}{5^2 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 6^2}$$

$$5646 := \frac{5^7 + 6^7 + 4^0 + 6^7}{5^2 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 6^2}$$

$$5647 := \frac{5^2 + 6^7 + 4^9 + 7^1}{5^2 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 7^2}$$

$$5647 := \frac{5^2 + 6^7 + 4^9 + 7^1}{5^2 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 7^2}$$

$$5648 := \frac{5^4 - 6^0 + 4^7 - 8^2}{-5^0 - 6^0 + 4^1 + 8^0}$$

$$5649 := \frac{5^7 + 6^7 + 4^{11} + 9^3}{5^2 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 9^3}$$

$$5649 := \frac{5^7 + 6^7 + 4^{11} + 9^3}{5^2 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 9^3}$$

$$5651 := \frac{-5^1 + 6^5 + 5^9 + 1^0}{5^1 + 6^3 + 5^3 + 1^0}$$

$$5652 := \frac{-5^3 + 6^6 + 5^6 + 2^4}{5^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 2^3}$$

$$5653 := \frac{5^3 + 6^3 + 5^5 + 3^7}{-5^0 + 6^1 - 5^0 - 3^1}$$

$$5654 := \frac{5^{11} + 6^3 + 5^{11} + 4^7}{5^4 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 4^5}$$

$$5654 := \frac{5^{11} + 6^3 + 5^{11} + 4^7}{5^4 + 6^0 + 5^6 + 4^5}$$

$$5655 := \frac{-5^0 + 6^9 + 5^7 - 5^{10}}{5^1 - 6^2 - 5^2 + 5^3}$$

$$5656 := \frac{-5^8 - 6^3 + 5^{10} - 6^7}{-5^1 - 6^3 + 5^5 - 6^4}$$

$$5657 := \frac{5^3 + 6^1 + 5^5 + 7^4}{-5^0 - 6^1 + 5^0 + 7^1}$$

$$5658 := \frac{5^0 - 6^3 + 5^8 - 8^1}{-5^0 + 6^0 + 5^1 + 8^2}$$

$$5659 := \frac{-5^2 + 6^4 + 5^6 + 9^2}{-5^0 + 6^1 - 5^0 - 9^0}$$

$$5662 := \frac{5^8 + 6^0 + 6^2 + 2^4}{5^2 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 2^5}$$

$$5662 := \frac{5^8 + 6^0 + 6^2 + 2^4}{5^2 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 2^5}$$

$$5663 := \frac{5^0 + 6^2 + 6^8 + 3^{16}}{5^1 + 6^2 + 6^4 + 3^8}$$

$$5663 := \frac{5^0 + 6^2 + 6^8 + 3^{16}}{5^1 + 6^2 + 6^4 + 3^8}$$

$$5664 := \frac{-5^8 + 6^7 + 6^8 + 4^0}{-5^0 + 6^1 + 6^4 - 4^5}$$

$$5665 := \frac{5^6 - 6^2 + 6^8 + 5^6}{5^2 + 6^2 + 6^3 + 5^2}$$

$$5667 := \frac{-5^2 - 6^4 + 6^6 + 7^0}{5^1 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5668 := \frac{5^6 - 6^0 - 6^2 + 8^6}{-5^0 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 8^1}$$

$$5669 := \frac{5^0 - 6^4 + 6^6 - 9^1}{5^1 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 9^0}$$

$$5670 := \frac{-5^6 + 6^2 + 7^6 + 0^1}{5^1 + 6^1 + 7^1 + 0^1}$$

$$5672 := \frac{5^7 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 2^1}{5^0 + 6^1 + 7^1 + 2^3}$$

$$5672 := \frac{5^7 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 2^1}{5^0 + 6^1 + 7^1 + 2^3}$$

$$5673 := \frac{5^7 + 6^1 + 7^1 + 3^{11}}{5^0 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 3^0}$$

$$5673 := \frac{5^7 + 6^1 + 7^1 + 3^{11}}{5^0 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 3^0}$$

$$5674 := \frac{5^4 + 6^4 - 7^3 + 4^6}{-5^0 - 6^0 - 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5675 := \frac{5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5 + 5^0}{-5^0 + 6^1 - 7^0 - 5^0}$$

$$5676 := \frac{5^5 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 6^6}{5^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 6^1}$$

$$5676 := \frac{5^5 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 6^6}{5^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 6^1}$$

$$5677 := \frac{5^6 + 6^9 + 7^1 + 7^7}{5^4 + 6^4 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5677 := \frac{5^6 + 6^9 + 7^1 + 7^7}{5^4 + 6^4 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5678 := \frac{5^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 8^2}{5^1 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 8^0}$$

$$5678 := \frac{5^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 8^2}{5^1 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 8^0}$$

$$5679 := \frac{5^5 + 6^7 + 7^1 + 9^4}{5^1 + 6^2 + 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$5679 := \frac{5^5 + 6^7 + 7^1 + 9^4}{5^1 + 6^2 + 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$5680 := \frac{5^8 + 6^4 - 8^0 + 0^1}{5^2 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 0^1}$$

$$5682 := \frac{5^8 + 6^5 + 8^0 + 2^{14}}{5^0 + 6^1 + 8^2 + 2^1}$$

$$5682 := \frac{5^8 + 6^5 + 8^0 + 2^{14}}{5^0 + 6^1 + 8^2 + 2^1}$$

$$5683 := \frac{5^2 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 3^2}{5^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^1}$$

$$5683 := \frac{5^2 + 6^4 + 8^5 + 3^2}{5^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^1}$$

$$5684 := \frac{5^6 + 6^7 + 8^1 - 4^0}{-5^0 + 6^2 + 8^0 + 4^2}$$

$$5685 := \frac{5^1 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 5^9}{-5^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 5^0}$$

$$5686 := \frac{5^2 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 6^7}{5^1 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 6^2}$$

$$5686 := \frac{5^2 + 6^0 + 8^5 + 6^7}{5^1 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 6^2}$$

$$5687 := \frac{-5^5 - 6^4 + 8^3 + 7^6}{5^1 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$5689 := \frac{5^7 + 6^5 - 8^4 - 9^5}{5^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$5691 := \frac{5^5 + 6^2 + 9^7 + 1^0}{5^4 + 6^3 - 9^0 + 1^0}$$

$$5692 := \frac{5^8 + 6^1 + 9^4 + 2^{20}}{5^1 + 6^3 + 9^0 + 2^5}$$

$$5692 := \frac{5^8 + 6^1 + 9^4 + 2^{20}}{5^1 + 6^3 + 9^0 + 2^5}$$

$$5693 := \frac{-5^4 - 6^3 + 9^4 - 3^3}{-5^0 + 6^1 - 9^0 - 3^1}$$

$$5694 := \frac{5^9 + 6^8 + 9^3 + 4^7}{5^4 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 4^0}$$

$$5694 := \frac{5^9 + 6^8 + 9^3 + 4^7}{5^4 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 4^0}$$

$$5695 := \frac{-5^2 - 6^3 + 9^4 - 5^4}{5^0 - 6^1 + 9^0 + 5^1}$$

$$5696 := \frac{-5^4 - 6^3 + 9^1 + 6^7}{5^1 - 6^0 + 9^1 + 6^2}$$

$$5697 := \frac{5^9 + 6^3 + 9^3 + 7^0}{5^3 + 6^3 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5697 := \frac{5^9 + 6^3 + 9^3 + 7^0}{5^3 + 6^3 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5698 := \frac{5^1 + 6^7 + 9^4 + 8^4}{5^1 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 8^0}$$

$$5698 := \frac{5^1 + 6^7 + 9^4 + 8^4}{5^1 + 6^2 + 9^1 + 8^0}$$

$$5699 := \frac{5^3 + 6^7 - 9^2 - 9^3}{5^2 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 9^1}$$

$$5702 := \frac{5^2 + 7^2 + 0^1 + 2^{17}}{5^1 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 2^4}$$

$$5702 := \frac{5^2 + 7^2 + 0^1 + 2^{17}}{5^1 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 2^4}$$

$$5703 := \frac{5^7 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 3^{10}}{5^2 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 3^0}$$

$$5703 := \frac{5^7 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 3^{10}}{5^2 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 3^0}$$

$$5704 := \frac{5^4 + 7^7 + 0^1 - 4^8}{5^3 + 7^1 + 0^1 + 4^0}$$

$$5706 := \frac{5^7 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 6^5}{5^1 + 7^1 + 0^1 + 6^1}$$

$$5706 := \frac{5^7 + 7^5 + 0^1 + 6^5}{5^1 + 7^1 + 0^1 + 6^1}$$

$$5707 := \frac{-5^7 - 7^6 + 0^0 + 7^7}{5^3 - 7^1 - 0^0 - 7^1}$$

$$5713 := \frac{5^9 - 7^1 - 1^0 + 3^6}{-5^0 + 7^3 - 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$5720 := \frac{-5^0 + 7^6 + 2^{13} + 0^1}{5^1 + 7^0 + 2^4 + 0^1}$$

$$5721 := \frac{-5^4 + 7^6 - 2^{16} + 1^0}{5^1 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 1^0}$$

$$5722 := \frac{5^5 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 2^{16}}{5^0 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 2^3}$$

$$5722 := \frac{5^5 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 2^{16}}{5^0 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 2^3}$$

$$5723 := \frac{5^4 + 7^0 + 2^{16} + 3^9}{5^0 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 3^2}$$

$$5723 := \frac{5^4 + 7^0 + 2^{16} + 3^9}{5^0 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 3^2}$$

$5724 := \frac{5^7 + 7^6 + 2^1 + 4^9}{5^0 + 7^1 + 2^3 + 4^3}$	$5736 := \frac{5^7 - 7^1 + 3^7 - 6^0}{5^1 + 7^1 + 3^0 + 6^0}$	$5748 := \frac{5^3 + 7^7 + 4^2 + 8^5}{5^3 + 7^1 + 4^2 + 8^0}$
$5724 := \frac{5^7 + 7^6 + 2^1 + 4^9}{5^0 + 7^1 + 2^3 + 4^3}$	$5737 := \frac{5^7 - 7^0 + 3^7 + 7^1}{5^1 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 7^1}$	$5749 := \frac{5^5 + 7^4 + 4^9 + 9^6}{5^1 + 7^2 + 4^1 + 9^2}$
$5725 := \frac{5^5 + 7^1 + 2^{15} + 5^6}{5^0 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 5^1}$	$5738 := \frac{-5^8 + 7^9 + 3^7 + 8^0}{5^3 + 7^3 + 3^8 - 8^2}$	$5749 := \frac{5^5 + 7^4 + 4^9 + 9^6}{5^1 + 7^2 + 4^1 + 9^2}$
$5725 := \frac{5^5 + 7^1 + 2^{15} + 5^6}{5^0 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 5^1}$	$5739 := \frac{5^3 + 7^9 + 3^7 + 9^3}{5^3 + 7^3 + 3^1 + 9^4}$	$5750 := \frac{-5^2 + 7^4 + 5^7 - 0^0}{5^0 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 0^0}$
$5726 := \frac{5^3 + 7^6 + 2^{13} + 6^1}{5^0 + 7^1 + 2^3 + 6^1}$	$5739 := \frac{5^3 + 7^9 + 3^7 + 9^3}{5^3 + 7^3 + 3^1 + 9^4}$	$5752 := \frac{5^0 + 7^4 + 5^7 + 2^0}{5^0 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 2^0}$
$5726 := \frac{5^3 + 7^6 + 2^{13} + 6^1}{5^0 + 7^1 + 2^3 + 6^1}$	$5740 := \frac{5^6 - 7^2 - 4^6 + 0^1}{-5^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$	$5752 := \frac{5^0 + 7^4 + 5^7 + 2^0}{5^0 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 2^0}$
$5727 := \frac{-5^0 + 7^3 + 2^5 + 7^5}{-5^0 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$	$5741 := \frac{-5^6 + 7^3 + 4^9 + 1^0}{5^2 + 7^0 + 4^2 + 1^0}$	$5753 := \frac{5^2 + 7^4 + 5^7 - 3^2}{5^0 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 3^0}$
$5728 := \frac{5^0 - 7^4 + 2^{13} - 8^2}{-5^0 - 7^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$	$5742 := \frac{5^3 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 2^{15}}{5^1 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$	$5754 := \frac{-5^7 + 7^9 + 5^9 - 4^0}{5^3 - 7^1 + 5^5 + 4^6}$
$5729 := \frac{5^6 + 7^6 + 2^{13} + 9^5}{5^0 + 7^0 + 2^5 + 9^0}$	$5742 := \frac{5^3 + 7^4 + 4^7 + 2^{15}}{5^1 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$	$5757 := \frac{-5^0 + 7^7 + 5^{10} - 7^8}{-5^0 - 7^3 - 5^6 + 7^5}$
$5729 := \frac{5^6 + 7^6 + 2^{13} + 9^5}{5^0 + 7^0 + 2^5 + 9^0}$	$5743 := \frac{5^0 + 7^4 + 4^4 + 3^{12}}{5^0 + 7^0 + 4^3 + 3^3}$	$5758 := \frac{-5^0 + 7^6 + 5^7 - 8^0}{5^0 + 7^1 + 5^2 + 8^0}$
$5730 := \frac{5^4 + 7^5 - 3^5 + 0^0}{5^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$	$5743 := \frac{5^0 + 7^4 + 4^4 + 3^{12}}{5^0 + 7^0 + 4^3 + 3^3}$	$5759 := \frac{-5^6 - 7^1 - 5^7 + 9^6}{5^0 + 7^2 + 5^2 + 9^0}$
$5731 := \frac{5^6 - 7^9 + 3^{19} - 1^0}{5^7 + 7^6 - 3^2 - 1^0}$	$5744 := \frac{5^4 - 7^0 + 4^5 + 4^6}{-5^0 - 7^0 - 4^0 + 4^1}$	$5760 := \frac{-5^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 0^1}{5^0 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 0^1}$
$5732 := \frac{5^6 + 7^4 - 3^8 - 2^0}{-5^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$	$5745 := \frac{5^1 + 7^6 + 4^{10} + 5^1}{5^2 + 7^2 + 4^1 + 5^3}$	$5761 := \frac{-5^7 + 7^8 - 6^6 - 1^0}{5^2 - 7^3 + 6^4 + 1^0}$
$5733 := \frac{5^9 + 7^4 + 3^1 + 3^{11}}{5^0 + 7^3 + 3^0 + 3^3}$	$5745 := \frac{5^1 + 7^6 + 4^{10} + 5^1}{5^2 + 7^2 + 4^1 + 5^3}$	$5762 := \frac{5^7 + 7^6 + 6^1 + 2^7}{5^1 + 7^1 + 6^1 + 2^4}$
$5733 := \frac{5^9 + 7^4 + 3^1 + 3^{11}}{5^0 + 7^3 + 3^0 + 3^3}$	$5746 := \frac{5^5 + 7^4 + 4^1 + 6^3}{-5^0 - 7^0 + 4^1 - 6^0}$	$5762 := \frac{5^7 + 7^6 + 6^1 + 2^7}{5^1 + 7^1 + 6^1 + 2^4}$
$5734 := \frac{-5^7 + 7^7 + 3^0 + 4^0}{5^3 + 7^0 + 3^1 + 4^0}$	$5747 := \frac{5^7 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 7^1}{5^0 + 7^0 + 4^2 + 7^1}$	$5763 := \frac{5^5 + 7^6 + 6^1 + 3^5}{5^1 + 7^1 + 6^1 + 3^1}$
$5735 := \frac{5^3 + 7^1 + 3^9 + 5^5}{5^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$	$5747 := \frac{5^7 + 7^1 + 4^8 + 7^1}{5^0 + 7^0 + 4^2 + 7^1}$	$5763 := \frac{5^5 + 7^6 + 6^1 + 3^5}{5^1 + 7^1 + 6^1 + 3^1}$
$5735 := \frac{5^3 + 7^1 + 3^9 + 5^5}{5^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$	$5748 := \frac{5^3 + 7^7 + 4^2 + 8^5}{5^3 + 7^1 + 4^2 + 8^0}$	$5764 := \frac{5^2 + 7^3 + 6^7 + 4^8}{5^0 + 7^1 + 6^2 + 4^2}$

$5764 := \frac{5^2 + 7^3 + 6^7 + 4^8}{5^0 + 7^1 + 6^2 + 4^2}$	$5783 := \frac{5^3 + 7^3 + 8^4 + 3^{10}}{5^0 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 3^0}$	$5804 := \frac{-5^7 - 8^4 + 0^0 + 4^9}{5^2 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 4^1}$
$5765 := \frac{5^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 5^9}{5^1 + 7^0 + 6^3 + 5^3}$	$5783 := \frac{5^3 + 7^3 + 8^4 + 3^{10}}{5^0 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 3^0}$	$5809 := \frac{-5^8 - 8^6 - 0^0 + 9^7}{-5^2 + 8^1 - 0^0 + 9^3}$
$5765 := \frac{5^4 + 7^2 + 6^6 + 5^9}{5^1 + 7^0 + 6^3 + 5^3}$	$5784 := \frac{5^4 + 7^3 + 8^5 - 4^7}{-5^0 - 7^0 + 8^0 + 4^1}$	$5812 := \frac{5^6 + 8^6 - 1^0 + 2^{19}}{5^0 + 8^1 + 1^0 + 2^7}$
$5766 := \frac{5^7 + 7^1 + 6^4 + 6^4}{5^0 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 6^1}$	$5785 := \frac{-5^5 + 7^6 + 8^4 - 5^7}{-5^0 - 7^0 + 8^1 + 5^0}$	$5814 := \frac{5^8 - 8^2 + 1^0 - 4^5}{5^0 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 4^3}$
$5767 := \frac{-5^2 - 7^0 + 6^6 + 7^5}{-5^0 - 7^0 + 6^1 + 7^1}$	$5786 := \frac{5^6 + 7^1 - 8^4 + 6^2}{-5^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 6^0}$	$5820 := \frac{5^2 - 8^3 + 2^{19} - 0^0}{5^2 + 8^0 + 2^6 + 0^1}$
$5768 := \frac{5^7 + 7^1 + 6^2 + 8^6}{5^0 + 7^2 + 6^0 + 8^1}$	$5787 := \frac{5^4 - 7^1 - 8^2 + 7^5}{5^0 + 7^0 + 8^1 - 7^1}$	$5822 := \frac{-5^2 - 8^0 - 2^7 + 2^{18}}{5^0 + 8^1 + 2^2 + 2^5}$
$5768 := \frac{5^7 + 7^1 + 6^2 + 8^6}{5^0 + 7^2 + 6^0 + 8^1}$	$5788 := \frac{5^0 + 7^1 + 8^4 + 8^6}{-5^0 + 7^2 - 8^0 - 8^0}$	$5823 := \frac{5^4 + 8^4 + 2^{14} + 3^7}{5^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$
$5769 := \frac{5^9 + 7^6 + 6^3 + 9^2}{5^0 + 7^3 + 6^1 + 9^1}$	$5789 := \frac{5^4 + 7^5 - 8^2 - 9^0}{5^0 + 7^0 - 8^1 + 9^1}$	$5823 := \frac{5^4 + 8^4 + 2^{14} + 3^7}{5^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$
$5769 := \frac{5^9 + 7^6 + 6^3 + 9^2}{5^0 + 7^3 + 6^1 + 9^1}$	$5792 := \frac{-5^8 - 7^6 + 9^6 + 2^0}{5^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$	$5824 := \frac{-5^0 + 8^0 - 2^6 + 4^9}{5^0 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 4^1}$
$5770 := \frac{5^9 + 7^4 - 7^5 + 0^0}{-5^0 - 7^1 + 7^3 + 0^0}$	$5793 := \frac{-5^9 - 7^9 - 9^6 + 3^{16}}{5^0 + 7^1 + 9^0 + 3^3}$	$5825 := \frac{5^7 + 8^0 + 2^{10} + 5^7}{5^1 + 8^0 + 2^4 + 5^1}$
$5773 := \frac{-5^0 - 7^0 + 7^6 - 3^7}{5^1 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 3^0}$	$5795 := \frac{5^3 + 7^4 - 9^4 + 5^6}{-5^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 5^0}$	$5825 := \frac{5^7 + 8^0 + 2^{10} + 5^7}{5^1 + 8^0 + 2^4 + 5^1}$
$5774 := \frac{5^8 - 7^3 + 7^8 + 4^0}{5^5 + 7^3 - 7^4 - 4^0}$	$5796 := \frac{5^{11} - 7^9 - 9^4 - 6^0}{5^1 + 7^4 - 9^3 - 6^3}$	$5826 := \frac{5^0 + 8^0 + 2^{12} + 6^8}{5^0 + 8^1 + 2^6 + 6^3}$
$5775 := \frac{5^4 - 7^2 + 7^6 + 5^7}{5^0 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 5^2}$	$5797 := \frac{5^3 + 7^2 + 9^6 + 7^6}{5^1 + 7^2 + 9^1 + 7^2}$	$5826 := \frac{5^0 + 8^0 + 2^{12} + 6^8}{5^0 + 8^1 + 2^6 + 6^3}$
$5776 := \frac{5^5 - 7^5 + 7^6 + 6^0}{5^1 + 7^1 + 7^1 - 6^0}$	$5797 := \frac{5^3 + 7^2 + 9^6 + 7^6}{5^1 + 7^2 + 9^1 + 7^2}$	$5827 := \frac{5^7 - 8^1 - 2^{13} - 7^0}{5^0 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 7^0}$
$5779 := \frac{-5^6 + 7^4 + 7^7 - 9^5}{-5^0 + 7^0 + 7^2 + 9^2}$	$5798 := \frac{5^6 + 7^6 + 9^2 - 8^0}{5^1 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 8^1}$	$5828 := \frac{5^6 - 8^0 + 2^7 - 8^4}{-5^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$
$5780 := \frac{5^1 - 7^6 + 8^6 + 0^1}{5^2 - 7^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$	$5799 := \frac{5^6 - 7^2 + 9^4 + 9^5}{5^1 + 7^1 + 9^0 + 9^0}$	$5829 := \frac{5^6 - 8^4 + 2^7 + 9^0}{-5^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 9^0}$
$5781 := \frac{5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3 - 1^0}{5^0 - 7^1 + 8^1 + 1^0}$	$5802 := \frac{5^7 + 8^6 + 0^0 + 2^{11}}{5^2 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 2^5}$	$5830 := \frac{5^5 + 8^3 + 3^9 + 0^1}{5^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 0^0}$
$5782 := \frac{-5^0 - 7^4 - 8^1 + 2^{13}}{-5^0 - 7^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$	$5802 := \frac{5^7 + 8^6 + 0^0 + 2^{11}}{5^2 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 2^5}$	$5830 := \frac{5^5 + 8^3 + 3^9 + 0^1}{5^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 0^0}$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 5832 := \frac{5^5 + 8^1 + 3^9 + 2^9}{5^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 2^0} & 5844 := \frac{5^3 - 8^0 + 4^5 + 4^7}{-5^0 - 8^0 + 4^0 + 4^1} & 5866 := \frac{5^6 + 8^2 - 6^0 + 6^5}{5^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 6^0} \\
 5833 := \frac{5^8 + 8^4 + 3^2 + 3^{13}}{5^2 + 8^2 + 3^2 + 3^5} & 5845 := \frac{5^5 - 8^2 + 4^7 + 5^6}{-5^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 5^1} & 5867 := \frac{5^0 - 8^2 + 6^6 + 7^3}{5^1 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 7^0} \\
 5834 := \frac{5^5 + 8^3 + 3^9 + 4^2}{5^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 4^0} & 5846 := \frac{5^6 - 8^0 - 4^2 + 6^5}{5^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 6^0} & 5868 := \frac{-5^6 - 8^2 + 6^0 + 8^6}{5^2 + 8^1 + 6^0 + 8^1} \\
 5834 := \frac{5^5 + 8^3 + 3^9 + 4^2}{5^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 4^0} & 5847 := \frac{5^2 + 8^5 + 4^7 - 7^4}{5^1 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 7^0} & 5869 := \frac{-5^3 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 9^1}{-5^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 9^0} \\
 5835 := \frac{-5^0 + 8^5 - 3^3 + 5^7}{5^0 + 8^1 + 3^2 + 5^0} & 5849 := \frac{5^9 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 9^8}{5^4 + 8^3 + 4^1 + 9^4} & 5871 := \frac{-5^4 + 8^4 + 7^4 - 1^0}{5^0 - 8^1 + 7^1 + 1^0} \\
 5836 := \frac{5^2 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 6^2}{5^0 + 8^0 + 3^1 + 6^0} & 5849 := \frac{5^9 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 9^8}{5^4 + 8^3 + 4^1 + 9^4} & 5872 := \frac{5^6 + 8^3 + 7^7 + 2^4}{5^3 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 2^4} \\
 5836 := \frac{5^2 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 6^2}{5^0 + 8^0 + 3^1 + 6^0} & 5852 := \frac{-5^3 + 8^3 + 5^5 + 2^{13}}{-5^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 2^0} & 5872 := \frac{5^6 + 8^3 + 7^7 + 2^4}{5^3 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 2^4} \\
 5837 := \frac{5^7 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 7^1}{5^0 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 7^1} & 5853 := \frac{5^2 + 8^4 + 5^6 - 3^7}{-5^0 + 8^1 - 5^0 - 3^1} & 5873 := \frac{5^8 + 8^3 + 7^1 + 3^{14}}{5^2 + 8^3 + 7^3 + 3^0} \\
 5837 := \frac{5^7 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 7^1}{5^0 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 7^1} & 5854 := \frac{-5^1 - 8^3 - 5^4 + 4^8}{5^0 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 4^1} & 5874 := \frac{5^7 + 8^1 + 7^1 + 4^6}{5^0 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 4^1} \\
 5838 := \frac{5^8 + 8^1 + 3^0 + 8^3}{5^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 8^2} & 5857 := \frac{5^7 - 8^3 + 5^7 + 7^4}{5^0 + 8^1 + 5^2 - 7^1} & 5874 := \frac{5^7 + 8^1 + 7^1 + 4^6}{5^0 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 4^1} \\
 5838 := \frac{5^8 + 8^1 + 3^0 + 8^3}{5^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 8^2} & 5858 := \frac{5^4 + 8^3 + 5^4 + 8^4}{-5^0 - 8^0 - 5^1 + 8^1} & 5875 := \frac{-5^2 + 8^0 + 7^6 - 5^3}{5^0 + 8^0 - 7^1 + 5^2} \\
 5839 := \frac{5^5 + 8^1 + 3^{11} + 9^3}{5^1 + 8^1 + 3^2 + 9^1} & 5859 := \frac{-5^2 + 8^5 - 5^6 + 9^5}{-5^0 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 9^0} & 5876 := \frac{5^0 + 8^1 + 7^3 + 6^6}{5^1 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 6^0} \\
 5839 := \frac{5^5 + 8^1 + 3^{11} + 9^3}{5^1 + 8^1 + 3^2 + 9^1} & 5862 := \frac{5^5 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 2^{20}}{5^3 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 2^4} & 5876 := \frac{5^0 + 8^1 + 7^3 + 6^6}{5^1 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 6^0} \\
 5840 := \frac{5^4 + 8^3 + 4^7 - 0^0}{5^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 0^1} & 5862 := \frac{5^5 + 8^5 + 6^0 + 2^{20}}{5^3 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 2^4} & 5877 := \frac{5^5 + 8^1 + 7^3 + 7^4}{5^0 - 8^1 + 7^0 + 7^1} \\
 5841 := \frac{5^8 - 8^4 - 4^5 + 1^0}{-5^0 + 8^2 + 4^1 - 1^0} & 5863 := \frac{5^8 + 8^1 + 6^0 + 3^7}{5^0 + 8^2 + 6^0 + 3^0} & 5878 := \frac{5^7 + 8^2 + 7^1 + 8^4}{5^1 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 8^0} \\
 5842 := \frac{5^3 + 8^0 + 4^{10} + 2^{20}}{-5^2 + 8^2 + 4^3 + 2^8} & 5863 := \frac{5^8 + 8^1 + 6^0 + 3^7}{5^0 + 8^2 + 6^0 + 3^0} & 5878 := \frac{5^7 + 8^2 + 7^1 + 8^4}{5^1 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 8^0} \\
 5843 := \frac{5^6 + 8^4 + 4^4 + 3^{14}}{5^2 + 8^2 + 4^1 + 3^6} & 5864 := \frac{-5^0 + 8^0 + 6^6 + 4^4}{5^1 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 4^0} & 5879 := \frac{-5^4 - 8^1 - 7^2 + 9^4}{-5^0 - 8^1 + 7^0 + 9^1} \\
 5843 := \frac{5^6 + 8^4 + 4^4 + 3^{14}}{5^2 + 8^2 + 4^1 + 3^6} & 5865 := \frac{-5^1 + 8^2 + 6^5 + 5^6}{5^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 5^0} & 5882 := \frac{-5^7 - 8^0 - 8^1 + 2^{17}}{5^1 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}
 \end{array}$$

$$5883 := \frac{5^9 + 8^5 - 8^6 - 3^{13}}{5^1 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 3^0}$$

$$5884 := \frac{5^8 - 8^0 + 8^5 + 4^4}{-5^0 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 4^3}$$

$$5886 := \frac{-5^5 + 8^0 + 8^6 - 6^2}{-5^0 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 6^2}$$

$$5887 := \frac{5^7 + 8^3 + 8^7 + 7^4}{5^2 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 7^3}$$

$$5887 := \frac{5^7 + 8^3 + 8^7 + 7^4}{5^2 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 7^3}$$

$$5889 := \frac{-5^8 + 8^1 + 8^3 + 9^6}{-5^0 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$5892 := \frac{-5^3 - 8^3 + 9^4 - 2^5}{-5^0 - 8^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5893 := \frac{5^3 + 8^6 + 9^3 + 3^7}{5^0 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 3^3}$$

$$5893 := \frac{5^3 + 8^6 + 9^3 + 3^7}{5^0 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 3^3}$$

$$5894 := \frac{5^5 - 8^5 + 9^5 + 4^3}{-5^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5895 := \frac{5^2 + 8^0 + 9^5 - 5^3}{-5^0 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$5896 := \frac{5^0 + 8^4 - 9^2 + 6^5}{-5^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$5897 := \frac{5^2 + 8^6 - 9^4 + 7^7}{5^3 + 8^1 + 9^0 + 7^2}$$

$$5898 := \frac{5^1 + 8^5 - 9^4 + 8^5}{-5^0 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 8^0}$$

$$5899 := \frac{-5^5 + 8^7 + 9^5 + 9^5}{5^2 + 8^3 - 9^2 - 9^2}$$

$$5902 := \frac{5^5 + 9^3 + 0^1 + 2^{11}}{-5^0 - 9^0 + 0^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5903 := \frac{5^7 - 9^3 + 0^0 - 3^8}{5^0 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 3^2}$$

$$5904 := \frac{-5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 - 4^1}{5^1 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 4^1}$$

$$5905 := \frac{5^6 + 9^3 + 0^0 + 5^7}{5^0 + 9^1 + 0^0 + 5^1}$$

$$5905 := \frac{5^6 + 9^3 + 0^0 + 5^7}{5^0 + 9^1 + 0^0 + 5^1}$$

$$5906 := \frac{5^1 + 9^5 + 0^1 + 6^1}{-5^0 + 9^1 + 0^0 + 6^0}$$

$$5907 := \frac{-5^5 + 9^4 + 0^0 + 7^7}{5^3 + 9^1 - 0^0 + 7^1}$$

$$5908 := \frac{5^{11} - 9^1 + 0^1 - 8^8}{-5^4 + 9^4 + 0^0 - 8^3}$$

$$5909 := \frac{-5^2 - 9^6 + 0^1 + 9^8}{5^4 + 9^1 + 0^1 + 9^4}$$

$$5913 := \frac{-5^0 + 9^2 + 1^0 + 3^{10}}{5^1 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 3^1}$$

$$5915 := \frac{-5^2 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 5^3}{-5^0 + 9^1 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$5920 := \frac{-5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 0^1}{-5^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 0^1}$$

$$5921 := \frac{-5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 1^0}{-5^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 1^0}$$

$$5921 := \frac{-5^4 + 9^4 - 2^4 + 1^4}{-5^1 + 9^1 - 2^1 - 1^1}$$

$$5922 := \frac{5^8 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 2^{16}}{5^0 + 9^2 + 2^0 + 2^2}$$

$$5922 := \frac{5^8 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 2^{16}}{5^0 + 9^2 + 2^0 + 2^2}$$

$$5923 := \frac{5^7 + 9^5 + 2^{19} + 3^9}{5^0 + 9^0 + 2^5 + 3^4}$$

$$5923 := \frac{5^7 + 9^5 + 2^{19} + 3^9}{5^0 + 9^0 + 2^5 + 3^4}$$

$$5924 := \frac{5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3}{5^0 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 4^1}$$

$$5924 := \frac{5^3 + 9^5 + 2^1 + 4^3}{5^0 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 4^1}$$

$$5925 := \frac{5^4 + 9^2 + 2^{18} + 5^6}{5^0 + 9^1 + 2^5 + 5^1}$$

$$5925 := \frac{5^4 + 9^2 + 2^{18} + 5^6}{5^0 + 9^1 + 2^5 + 5^1}$$

$$5926 := \frac{-5^4 + 9^4 - 2^2 - 6^1}{-5^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$5927 := \frac{5^0 + 9^4 + 2^{16} + 7^5}{5^0 + 9^1 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$5927 := \frac{5^0 + 9^4 + 2^{16} + 7^5}{5^0 + 9^1 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$5928 := \frac{-5^3 + 9^4 + 2^2 - 8^3}{-5^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$5929 := \frac{-5^4 + 9^0 - 2^3 + 9^4}{-5^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5930 := \frac{5^2 + 9^3 + 3^{11} - 0^0}{5^0 + 9^0 + 3^3 + 0^0}$$

$$5932 := \frac{-5^4 + 9^4 - 3^1 - 2^0}{-5^0 - 9^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5933 := \frac{-5^6 - 9^1 + 3^9 + 3^9}{5^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$5934 := \frac{5^3 + 9^5 + 3^{14} + 4^0}{5^1 + 9^2 + 3^6 + 4^0}$$

$$5934 := \frac{5^3 + 9^5 + 3^{14} + 4^0}{5^1 + 9^2 + 3^6 + 4^0}$$

$$5935 := \frac{-5^0 + 9^5 - 3^9 - 5^6}{5^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$5936 := \frac{-5^4 - 9^0 + 3^8 + 6^0}{-5^0 - 9^0 - 3^1 + 6^1}$$

$$5937 := \frac{5^5 + 9^4 + 3^7 + 7^0}{-5^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$5938 := \frac{-5^4 + 9^0 + 3^8 + 8^0}{5^0 + 9^0 - 3^2 + 8^1}$$

$$5939 := \frac{-5^2 + 9^4 - 3^{13} + 9^7}{5^4 - 9^1 + 3^1 - 9^2}$$

$$5940 := \frac{-5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 0^1}{-5^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$$

$$5941 := \frac{-5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 1^0}{-5^0 - 9^0 + 4^1 - 1^0}$$

$$5942 := \frac{5^7 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 2^{17}}{5^2 + 9^1 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5942 := \frac{5^7 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 2^{17}}{5^2 + 9^1 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$5943 := \frac{-5^4 - 9^1 + 4^2 + 3^8}{-5^0 - 9^0 + 4^1 - 3^0}$$

$$5944 := \frac{-5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 4^1}{-5^0 - 9^0 - 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5945 := \frac{5^9 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 5^9}{5^2 + 9^0 + 4^2 + 5^4}$$

$$5945 := \frac{5^9 + 9^5 + 4^2 + 5^9}{5^2 + 9^0 + 4^2 + 5^4}$$

$$5946 := \frac{5^7 + 9^2 + 4^1 + 6^6}{5^1 + 9^1 + 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$5946 := \frac{5^7 + 9^2 + 4^1 + 6^6}{5^1 + 9^1 + 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$5947 := \frac{5^7 + 9^0 + 4^9 + 7^6}{5^1 + 9^0 + 4^3 + 7^1}$$

$$5947 := \frac{5^7 + 9^0 + 4^9 + 7^6}{5^1 + 9^0 + 4^3 + 7^1}$$

$$5948 := \frac{-5^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 8^1}{-5^0 - 9^0 + 4^1 - 8^0}$$

$$5949 := \frac{-5^4 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 9^4}{-5^0 - 9^0 + 4^1 - 9^0}$$

$$5953 := \frac{5^1 + 9^2 + 5^8 + 3^7}{5^1 + 9^1 + 5^2 + 3^3}$$

$$5953 := \frac{5^1 + 9^2 + 5^8 + 3^7}{5^1 + 9^1 + 5^2 + 3^3}$$

$$5954 := \frac{5^1 - 9^3 + 5^7 + 4^0}{-5^0 - 9^0 - 5^0 + 4^2}$$

$$5955 := \frac{5^0 + 9^5 - 5^3 + 5^4}{-5^0 + 9^0 + 5^1 + 5^1}$$

$$5957 := \frac{-5^4 - 9^2 + 5^9 + 7^7}{-5^0 - 9^0 + 5^3 + 7^3}$$

$$5959 := \frac{5^2 - 9^2 + 5^7 - 9^4}{5^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 9^1}$$

$$5962 := \frac{5^0 + 9^1 + 6^2 + 2^{16}}{5^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 2^3}$$

$$5962 := \frac{5^0 + 9^1 + 6^2 + 2^{16}}{5^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 2^3}$$

$$5963 := \frac{5^0 + 9^2 + 6^7 + 3^5}{5^0 + 9^0 + 6^2 + 3^2}$$

$$5963 := \frac{5^0 + 9^2 + 6^7 + 3^5}{5^0 + 9^0 + 6^2 + 3^2}$$

$$5964 := \frac{-5^3 + 9^4 - 6^3 - 4^4}{-5^0 - 9^0 - 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5965 := \frac{-5^2 + 9^5 + 6^0 + 5^4}{-5^0 + 9^1 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$5966 := \frac{-5^4 + 9^4 - 6^1 + 6^2}{-5^0 + 9^1 - 6^0 - 6^1}$$

$$5967 := \frac{5^8 + 9^0 + 6^6 + 7^6}{5^1 + 9^2 + 6^1 + 7^0}$$

$$5967 := \frac{5^8 + 9^0 + 6^6 + 7^6}{5^1 + 9^2 + 6^1 + 7^0}$$

$$5968 := \frac{5^6 - 9^1 - 6^5 + 8^4}{-5^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$5969 := \frac{-5^2 + 9^3 - 6^4 + 9^4}{-5^0 - 9^0 - 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$5970 := \frac{5^9 - 9^4 - 7^3 - 0^0}{-5^2 + 9^1 + 7^3 - 0^0}$$

$$5972 := \frac{5^1 + 9^4 + 7^7 - 2^0}{5^0 + 9^1 + 7^0 + 2^7}$$

$$5973 := \frac{5^5 + 9^3 + 7^6 + 3^{11}}{5^2 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 3^2}$$

$$5973 := \frac{5^5 + 9^3 + 7^6 + 3^{11}}{5^2 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 3^2}$$

$$5974 := \frac{5^4 - 9^6 + 7^7 - 4^0}{5^2 + 9^0 + 7^1 + 4^2}$$

$$5975 := \frac{5^6 + 9^0 + 7^2 + 5^8}{5^1 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 5^1}$$

$$5975 := \frac{5^6 + 9^0 + 7^2 + 5^8}{5^1 + 9^1 + 7^2 + 5^1}$$

$$5977 := \frac{-5^2 - 9^5 + 7^4 + 7^9}{5^3 + 9^4 + 7^1 + 7^2}$$

$$5978 := \frac{5^{13} - 9^2 + 7^7 - 8^0}{5^8 + 9^5 + 7^5 - 8^6}$$

$$5979 := \frac{5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5}{5^0 + 9^0 + 7^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5979 := \frac{5^1 + 9^3 + 7^1 + 9^5}{5^0 + 9^0 + 7^1 + 9^0}$$

$$5982 := \frac{5^5 + 9^0 + 8^5 - 2^1}{-5^0 + 9^0 + 8^1 - 2^1}$$

$$5983 := \frac{5^9 + 9^0 + 8^4 + 3^{10}}{5^1 + 9^2 + 8^1 + 3^5}$$

$$5983 := \frac{5^9 + 9^0 + 8^4 + 3^{10}}{5^1 + 9^2 + 8^1 + 3^5}$$

$$5984 := \frac{-5^0 + 9^4 - 8^3 - 4^3}{-5^0 - 9^0 - 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$5985 := \frac{5^7 - 9^4 - 8^2 + 5^7}{5^0 - 9^1 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$5986 := \frac{-5^0 + 9^1 + 8^6 - 6^6}{5^2 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$5987 := \frac{5^3 + 9^7 + 8^3 + 7^1}{5^1 + 9^3 + 8^2 + 7^0}$$

$$5987 := \frac{5^3 + 9^7 + 8^3 + 7^1}{5^1 + 9^3 + 8^2 + 7^0}$$

$$5988 := \frac{-5^3 + 9^4 + 8^2 - 8^3}{5^0 - 9^1 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$5989 := \frac{5^7 + 9^4 + 8^0 + 9^5}{5^1 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 9^1}$$

$$5989 := \frac{5^7 + 9^4 + 8^0 + 9^5}{5^1 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 9^1}$$

$$5993 := \frac{5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3}{5^1 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 3^1}$$

$$5993 := \frac{5^3 + 9^3 + 9^5 + 3^3}{5^1 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 3^1}$$

$$5995 := \frac{-5^5 - 9^4 + 9^6 - 5^7}{-5^0 - 9^0 + 9^2 - 5^1}$$

$5997 := \frac{5^7 - 9^3 + 9^4 + 7^0}{5^1 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 7^1}$	$6035 := \frac{6^4 + 0^1 + 3^{10} + 5^1}{6^0 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 5^1}$	$6054 := \frac{6^6 - 0^0 - 5^0 - 4^7}{-6^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 4^1}$
$5999 := \frac{-5^2 + 9^3 + 9^6 + 9^7}{-5^1 + 9^2 + 9^2 + 9^3}$	$6035 := \frac{6^4 + 0^1 + 3^{10} + 5^1}{6^0 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 5^1}$	$6055 := \frac{-6^2 + 0^0 + 5^4 + 5^7}{6^1 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 5^1}$
$6023 := \frac{6^5 + 0^1 - 2^{10} - 3^6}{-6^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$	$6037 := \frac{6^4 - 0^0 + 3^2 + 7^5}{6^0 + 0^1 + 3^0 + 7^0}$	$6056 := \frac{-6^5 - 0^0 + 5^6 + 6^6}{6^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 6^1}$
$6024 := \frac{6^6 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 4^5}{6^0 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 4^1}$	$6038 := \frac{6^7 + 0^1 - 3^7 - 8^0}{6^2 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 8^1}$	$6063 := \frac{6^{10} + 0^1 + 6^{10} - 3^{13}}{-6^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 3^9}$
$6024 := \frac{6^6 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 4^5}{6^0 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 4^1}$	$6039 := \frac{-6^0 + 0^0 - 3^2 + 9^6}{6^1 + 0^1 + 3^0 + 9^2}$	$6072 := \frac{6^5 + 0^0 + 7^3 - 2^{11}}{-6^0 - 0^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$
$6025 := \frac{6^7 + 0^0 + 2^{19} + 5^5}{6^0 + 0^1 + 2^3 + 5^3}$	$6040 := \frac{6^5 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 0^1}{6^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$	$6073 := \frac{-6^8 - 0^0 - 7^2 + 3^{14}}{-6^3 - 0^0 - 7^0 + 3^6}$
$6025 := \frac{6^7 + 0^0 + 2^{19} + 5^5}{6^0 + 0^1 + 2^3 + 5^3}$	$6040 := \frac{6^5 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 0^1}{6^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$	$6077 := \frac{6^3 - 0^0 - 7^4 + 7^6}{6^1 - 0^0 + 7^1 + 7^1}$
$6026 := \frac{6^4 + 0^1 + 2^8 + 6^6}{6^0 + 0^1 + 2^0 + 6^1}$	$6042 := \frac{6^5 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 2^3}{6^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$	$6079 := \frac{-6^0 + 0^1 + 7^9 + 9^7}{6^5 + 0^0 - 7^3 - 9^1}$
$6026 := \frac{6^4 + 0^1 + 2^8 + 6^6}{6^0 + 0^1 + 2^0 + 6^1}$	$6042 := \frac{6^5 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 2^3}{6^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$	$6080 := \frac{6^6 - 0^0 - 8^4 + 0^0}{6^1 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 0^1}$
$6027 := \frac{6^{10} + 0^0 - 2^7 + 7^9}{6^0 + 0^1 + 2^{14} + 7^3}$	$6043 := \frac{6^8 - 0^0 - 4^1 - 3^{12}}{-6^2 - 0^0 - 4^2 + 3^5}$	$6082 := \frac{-6^5 + 0^1 + 8^8 + 2^{16}}{-6^4 + 0^1 + 8^4 - 2^5}$
$6028 := \frac{-6^4 + 0^1 + 2^2 + 8^8}{-6^4 - 0^0 - 2^4 + 8^4}$	$6044 := \frac{6^5 + 0^1 + 4^2 + 4^7}{6^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$	$6083 := \frac{6^6 - 0^0 + 8^6 + 3^9}{6^2 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 3^2}$
$6029 := \frac{6^3 + 0^0 + 2^{10} + 9^5}{6^0 + 0^1 + 2^3 + 9^0}$	$6044 := \frac{6^5 + 0^1 + 4^2 + 4^7}{6^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$	$6084 := \frac{6^7 + 0^1 - 8^1 - 4^3}{6^2 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 4^0}$
$6029 := \frac{6^3 + 0^0 + 2^{10} + 9^5}{6^0 + 0^1 + 2^3 + 9^0}$	$6047 := \frac{6^7 + 0^0 - 4^8 - 7^6}{-6^0 + 0^1 + 4^2 + 7^0}$	$6085 := \frac{6^7 + 0^1 - 8^0 - 5^2}{6^2 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 5^0}$
$6031 := \frac{6^6 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 1^0}{6^0 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 1^0}$	$6049 := \frac{6^7 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 9^2}{6^2 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 9^1}$	$6087 := \frac{6^7 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 7^0}{6^2 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 7^0}$
$6031 := \frac{6^6 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 1^0}{6^0 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 1^0}$	$6049 := \frac{6^7 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 9^2}{6^2 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 9^1}$	$6087 := \frac{6^7 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 7^0}{6^2 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 7^0}$
$6032 := \frac{6^7 + 0^0 - 3^8 + 2^{12}}{6^2 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 2^3}$	$6052 := \frac{6^7 + 0^0 - 5^5 + 2^{20}}{6^3 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$	$6092 := \frac{6^7 + 0^0 - 9^3 + 2^{10}}{6^2 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^3}$
$6033 := \frac{6^6 + 0^1 - 3^1 + 3^{13}}{6^0 + 0^0 + 3^3 + 3^5}$	$6053 := \frac{6^4 + 0^1 + 5^8 + 3^9}{6^2 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 3^3}$	$6093 := \frac{6^9 + 0^1 + 9^8 + 3^{11}}{6^5 + 0^1 + 9^3 + 3^5}$
$6034 := \frac{6^4 - 0^0 + 3^{10} - 4^1}{6^1 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 4^0}$	$6053 := \frac{6^4 + 0^1 + 5^8 + 3^9}{6^2 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 3^3}$	$6093 := \frac{6^9 + 0^1 + 9^8 + 3^{11}}{6^5 + 0^1 + 9^3 + 3^5}$

$$6094 := \frac{-6^1 - 0^0 + 9^5 - 4^7}{6^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6098 := \frac{6^6 - 0^0 + 9^7 - 8^1}{-6^0 + 0^1 + 9^3 + 8^2}$$

$$6123 := \frac{-6^5 + 1^0 + 2^{19} + 3^{10}}{6^1 - 1^0 + 2^3 + 3^4}$$

$$6125 := \frac{6^8 + 1^0 + 2^3 + 5^8}{6^3 - 1^0 - 2^1 + 5^3}$$

$$6127 := \frac{6^9 + 1^0 + 2^9 - 7^8}{-6^4 + 1^0 + 2^{11} - 7^2}$$

$$6129 := \frac{-6^6 + 1^0 - 2^{18} + 9^7}{6^3 + 1^0 + 2^9 + 9^0}$$

$$6132 := \frac{-6^6 - 1^0 + 3^{10} - 2^7}{-6^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$6134 := \frac{-6^4 - 1^0 + 3^9 + 4^2}{-6^0 - 1^0 + 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6135 := \frac{6^{11} - 1^0 - 3^{12} + 5^0}{-6^1 + 1^0 + 3^{10} + 5^1}$$

$$6137 := \frac{6^5 + 1^0 + 3^{13} - 7^3}{6^3 - 1^0 - 3^1 + 7^2}$$

$$6138 := \frac{6^8 + 1^0 + 3^7 + 8^1}{6^1 - 1^0 - 3^5 + 8^3}$$

$$6142 := \frac{-6^0 - 1^0 + 4^6 + 2^{11}}{-6^0 - 1^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6143 := \frac{6^5 + 1^0 + 4^{10} + 3^5}{-6^1 - 1^0 - 4^3 + 3^5}$$

$$6144 := \frac{-6^0 + 1^0 - 4^6 + 4^7}{-6^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$6147 := \frac{6^5 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 7^5}{6^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$6147 := \frac{6^5 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 7^5}{6^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$6152 := \frac{6^7 - 1^0 + 5^8 + 2^3}{-6^0 + 1^0 + 5^3 - 2^4}$$

$$6153 := \frac{6^3 + 1^0 - 5^4 + 3^8}{6^1 - 1^0 - 5^0 - 3^1}$$

$$6154 := \frac{6^5 - 1^0 + 5^7 + 4^4}{6^1 - 1^0 + 5^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6158 := \frac{6^6 + 1^0 + 5^8 - 8^2}{6^0 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 8^2}$$

$$6159 := \frac{6^6 - 1^0 + 5^8 + 9^1}{6^2 + 1^0 + 5^2 + 9^1}$$

$$6166 := \frac{6^0 + 1^0 - 6^7 + 6^8}{6^1 - 1^0 + 6^1 + 6^3}$$

$$6175 := \frac{6^8 + 1^0 + 7^9 + 5^0}{6^5 - 1^0 - 7^3 - 5^4}$$

$$6176 := \frac{6^4 - 1^0 + 7^6 - 6^5}{6^1 - 1^0 + 7^1 + 6^1}$$

$$6179 := \frac{6^0 + 1^0 - 7^2 + 9^6}{-6^0 - 1^0 + 7^1 + 9^2}$$

$$6181 := \frac{-6^7 - 1^0 + 8^7 - 1^0}{-6^3 - 1^0 + 8^3 - 1^0}$$

$$6181 := \frac{-6^7 - 1^7 + 8^7 - 1^7}{-6^3 - 1^3 + 8^3 - 1^3}$$

$$6183 := \frac{-6^3 + 1^0 + 8^3 + 3^{12}}{-6^1 + 1^0 + 8^2 + 3^3}$$

$$6189 := \frac{6^6 + 1^0 - 8^6 + 9^7}{6^3 + 1^0 + 8^3 + 9^1}$$

$$6192 := \frac{-6^6 - 1^0 + 9^5 - 2^3}{-6^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$6194 := \frac{-6^6 - 1^0 + 9^5 - 4^1}{-6^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$6197 := \frac{6^7 + 1^0 - 9^3 - 7^3}{6^2 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$6198 := \frac{6^5 + 1^0 + 9^6 + 8^1}{-6^0 - 1^0 + 9^2 + 8^1}$$

$$6202 := \frac{6^7 - 2^4 + 0^1 - 2^{17}}{6^1 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 2^4}$$

$$6203 := \frac{6^7 - 2^{17} - 0^0 + 3^2}{6^1 + 2^3 + 0^0 + 3^2}$$

$$6204 := \frac{-6^5 - 2^2 + 0^1 + 4^9}{6^2 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6207 := \frac{-6^5 + 2^{14} + 0^1 - 7^4}{-6^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 7^0}$$

$$6208 := \frac{6^7 - 2^6 + 0^1 - 8^3}{6^2 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 8^1}$$

$$6209 := \frac{6^7 - 2^8 + 0^0 + 9^8}{-6^4 + 2^{13} + 0^0 + 9^2}$$

$$6213 := \frac{-6^6 + 2^5 + 1^0 + 3^{10}}{-6^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$6215 := \frac{6^{10} + 2^{19} + 1^0 + 5^7}{6^5 + 2^{11} + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$6215 := \frac{6^{10} + 2^{19} + 1^0 + 5^7}{6^5 + 2^{11} + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$6216 := \frac{-6^3 - 2^0 + 1^0 + 6^7}{6^1 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 6^2}$$

$$6217 := \frac{6^7 - 2^{17} + 1^0 + 7^3}{6^1 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 7^0}$$

$$6218 := \frac{6^7 - 2^7 + 1^0 + 8^0}{6^1 + 2^5 - 1^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6219 := \frac{-6^3 + 2^{18} - 1^0 - 9^3}{6^2 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 9^0}$$

$$6220 := \frac{6^7 - 2^2 - 2^5 + 0^1}{6^2 + 2^0 + 2^3 + 0^1}$$

$$6221 := \frac{6^7 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 1^0}{6^2 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 1^2}$$

$$6221 := \frac{6^7 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 1^0}{6^2 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 1^2}$$

$$6222 := \frac{6^8 + 2^2 + 2^6 + 2^8}{6^1 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 2^8}$$

$$6222 := \frac{6^8 + 2^2 + 2^6 + 2^8}{6^1 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 2^8}$$

$$6223 := \frac{6^1 + 2^3 + 2^{16} + 3^{11}}{6^1 + 2^1 + 2^2 + 3^3}$$

$$6223 := \frac{6^1 + 2^3 + 2^{16} + 3^{11}}{6^1 + 2^1 + 2^2 + 3^3}$$

$$6224 := \frac{6^6 + 2^6 + 2^{11} + 4^5}{6^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6224 := \frac{6^6 + 2^6 + 2^{11} + 4^5}{6^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6225 := \frac{6^7 + 2^5 + 2^5 + 5^3}{6^1 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 5^1}$$

$$6225 := \frac{6^7 + 2^5 + 2^5 + 5^3}{6^1 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 5^1}$$

$$6226 := \frac{6^3 + 2^1 + 2^4 + 6^7}{6^0 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 6^2}$$

$$6226 := \frac{6^3 + 2^1 + 2^4 + 6^7}{6^0 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 6^2}$$

$$6227 := \frac{6^7 + 2^4 + 2^8 + 7^1}{6^1 + 2^4 + 2^4 + 7^1}$$

$$6227 := \frac{6^7 + 2^4 + 2^8 + 7^1}{6^1 + 2^4 + 2^4 + 7^1}$$

$$6228 := \frac{6^7 + 2^2 + 2^8 + 8^2}{6^0 + 2^2 + 2^5 + 8^1}$$

$$6228 := \frac{6^7 + 2^2 + 2^8 + 8^2}{6^0 + 2^2 + 2^5 + 8^1}$$

$$6229 := \frac{6^7 + 2^5 + 2^8 + 9^2}{6^2 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 9^0}$$

$$6229 := \frac{6^7 + 2^5 + 2^8 + 9^2}{6^2 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 9^0}$$

$$6230 := \frac{6^0 + 2^{17} - 3^5 + 0^1}{6^0 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 0^0}$$

$$6231 := \frac{6^6 + 2^9 + 3^{11} + 1^0}{6^1 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 1^0}$$

$$6231 := \frac{6^6 + 2^9 + 3^{11} + 1^0}{6^1 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 1^0}$$

$$6232 := \frac{6^0 - 2^8 - 3^{10} + 2^{16}}{-6^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6233 := \frac{6^6 + 2^{16} + 3^0 + 3^0}{6^1 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 3^2}$$

$$6233 := \frac{6^6 + 2^{16} + 3^0 + 3^0}{6^1 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 3^2}$$

$$6234 := \frac{6^7 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^0}{6^0 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^2}$$

$$6234 := \frac{6^7 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^0}{6^0 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^2}$$

$$6235 := \frac{6^0 + 2^9 + 3^{11} + 5^6}{6^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 5^2}$$

$$6235 := \frac{6^0 + 2^9 + 3^{11} + 5^6}{6^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 5^2}$$

$$6236 := \frac{6^1 + 2^0 + 3^{14} + 6^2}{6^0 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 6^2}$$

$$6236 := \frac{6^1 + 2^0 + 3^{14} + 6^2}{6^0 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 6^2}$$

$$6237 := \frac{6^6 + 2^{15} + 3^{11} + 7^6}{6^0 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 7^2}$$

$$6237 := \frac{6^6 + 2^{15} + 3^{11} + 7^6}{6^0 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 7^2}$$

$$6238 := \frac{6^9 + 2^2 + 3^{10} + 8^0}{6^4 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^2}$$

$$6238 := \frac{6^9 + 2^2 + 3^{10} + 8^0}{6^4 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^2}$$

$$6239 := \frac{-6^6 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 9^5}{-6^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$6240 := \frac{6^6 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 0^1}{6^0 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 0^1}$$

$$6240 := \frac{6^6 + 2^7 + 4^8 + 0^1}{6^0 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 0^1}$$

$$6241 := \frac{6^5 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 1^0}{-6^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 - 1^0}$$

$$6242 := \frac{6^0 + 2^3 + 4^0 + 2^{17}}{6^0 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 2^1}$$

$$6242 := \frac{6^0 + 2^3 + 4^0 + 2^{17}}{6^0 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 2^1}$$

$$6243 := \frac{6^1 + 2^{17} + 4^2 + 3^2}{6^0 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 3^1}$$

$$6243 := \frac{6^1 + 2^{17} + 4^2 + 3^2}{6^0 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 3^1}$$

$$6244 := \frac{6^6 + 2^{15} + 4^6 + 4^7}{6^1 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6244 := \frac{6^6 + 2^{15} + 4^6 + 4^7}{6^1 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6245 := \frac{6^7 + 2^6 + 4^5 + 5^0}{6^2 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$6245 := \frac{6^7 + 2^6 + 4^5 + 5^0}{6^2 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$6246 := \frac{6^1 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 6^5}{-6^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 - 6^0}$$

$$6247 := \frac{6^2 + 2^{13} + 4^{10} + 7^7}{6^1 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 7^1}$$

$$6248 := \frac{6^8 + 2^3 + 4^5 + 8^2}{6^0 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 8^1}$$

$$6248 := \frac{6^8 + 2^3 + 4^5 + 8^2}{6^0 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 8^1}$$

$$6249 := \frac{6^6 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^5}{6^1 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 9^1}$$

$$6251 := \frac{-6^2 - 2^{16} + 5^8 - 1^0}{-6^1 + 2^5 + 5^2 + 1^0}$$

$$6252 := \frac{-6^6 + 2^0 - 5^3 + 2^{16}}{-6^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6253 := \frac{6^4 + 2^8 + 5^{10} + 3^2}{6^4 + 2^8 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$6253 := \frac{6^4 + 2^8 + 5^{10} + 3^2}{6^4 + 2^8 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$6254 := \frac{6^6 + 2^{15} + 5^9 + 4^0}{6^2 + 2^3 + 5^2 + 4^4}$$

$$6254 := \frac{6^6 + 2^{15} + 5^9 + 4^0}{6^2 + 2^3 + 5^2 + 4^4}$$

$$6255 := \frac{6^0 + 2^6 + 5^5 + 5^7}{6^0 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 5^1}$$

$$6255 := \frac{6^0 + 2^6 + 5^5 + 5^7}{6^0 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 5^1}$$

$$6256 := \frac{6^0 - 2^8 - 5^8 + 6^8}{-6^0 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 6^3}$$

$$6257 := \frac{6^6 + 2^4 + 5^7 + 7^3}{6^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 7^1}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 6257 := \frac{6^6 + 2^4 + 5^7 + 7^3}{6^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 7^1} & 6269 := \frac{6^3 - 2^5 + 6^8 + 9^4}{6^1 + 2^8 + 6^1 + 9^0} & 6282 := \frac{6^1 + 2^{19} + 8^3 + 2^{19}}{6^1 + 2^5 + 8^0 + 2^7} \\
 6258 := \frac{6^4 + 2^{13} + 5^7 - 8^0}{6^0 + 2^2 + 5^0 + 8^1} & 6270 := \frac{6^0 + 2^{12} + 7^7 + 0^1}{6^1 + 2^7 - 7^0 - 0^0} & 6283 := \frac{6^2 + 2^{17} + 8^0 + 3^9}{6^1 + 2^0 + 8^1 + 3^2} \\
 6259 := \frac{6^3 + 2^{13} + 5^7 + 9^7}{6^2 + 2^3 + 5^1 + 9^3} & 6271 := \frac{6^5 - 2^2 + 7^6 - 1^0}{6^1 + 2^3 + 7^1 - 1^0} & 6283 := \frac{6^2 + 2^{17} + 8^0 + 3^9}{6^1 + 2^0 + 8^1 + 3^2} \\
 6259 := \frac{6^3 + 2^{13} + 5^7 + 9^7}{6^2 + 2^3 + 5^1 + 9^3} & 6272 := \frac{-6^0 + 2^5 + 7^4 + 2^{14}}{-6^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 2^1} & 6284 := \frac{6^6 + 2^{17} + 8^1 + 4^9}{6^0 + 2^0 + 8^2 + 4^1} \\
 6260 := \frac{6^2 + 2^{19} + 6^5 + 0^1}{-6^1 + 2^7 - 6^2 - 0^0} & 6273 := \frac{6^5 + 2^3 + 7^6 + 3^3}{6^1 + 2^2 + 7^0 + 3^2} & 6284 := \frac{6^6 + 2^{17} + 8^1 + 4^9}{6^0 + 2^0 + 8^2 + 4^1} \\
 6261 := \frac{6^4 + 2^9 + 6^7 + 1^0}{6^1 + 2^1 + 6^2 + 1^0} & 6273 := \frac{6^5 + 2^3 + 7^6 + 3^3}{6^1 + 2^2 + 7^0 + 3^2} & 6285 := \frac{-6^6 + 2^{15} + 8^5 - 5^2}{-6^0 + 2^0 + 8^1 - 5^1} \\
 6261 := \frac{6^4 + 2^9 + 6^7 + 1^0}{6^1 + 2^1 + 6^2 + 1^0} & 6274 := \frac{6^5 + 2^9 + 7^5 + 4^0}{6^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 4^0} & 6286 := \frac{6^4 + 2^{14} + 8^8 + 6^4}{6^4 + 2^4 + 8^2 + 6^4} \\
 6262 := \frac{6^5 - 2^2 + 6^6 + 2^{13}}{6^0 + 2^0 + 6^1 + 2^1} & 6274 := \frac{6^5 + 2^9 + 7^5 + 4^0}{6^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 4^0} & 6286 := \frac{6^4 + 2^{14} + 8^8 + 6^4}{6^4 + 2^4 + 8^2 + 6^4} \\
 6263 := \frac{-6^1 - 2^8 - 6^2 + 3^8}{-6^0 - 2^0 + 6^1 - 3^1} & 6275 := \frac{6^5 + 2^9 + 7^5 + 5^1}{6^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 5^0} & 6287 := \frac{6^1 - 2^{11} + 8^4 + 7^5}{6^0 + 2^0 + 8^1 - 7^1} \\
 6264 := \frac{6^5 + 2^{13} + 6^6 + 4^2}{6^0 + 2^1 + 6^1 + 4^0} & 6275 := \frac{6^5 + 2^9 + 7^5 + 5^1}{6^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 5^0} & 6288 := \frac{6^5 + 2^{16} + 8^4 + 8^6}{6^1 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 8^1} \\
 6264 := \frac{6^5 + 2^{13} + 6^6 + 4^2}{6^0 + 2^1 + 6^1 + 4^0} & 6276 := \frac{-6^0 + 2^{17} - 7^5 - 6^4}{6^0 + 2^2 + 7^1 + 6^1} & 6288 := \frac{6^5 + 2^{16} + 8^4 + 8^6}{6^1 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 8^1} \\
 6265 := \frac{6^3 + 2^{15} + 6^5 + 5^6}{6^0 + 2^0 + 6^1 + 5^0} & 6277 := \frac{6^7 + 2^{19} + 7^5 + 7^7}{6^2 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 7^2} & 6289 := \frac{-6^3 + 2^3 - 8^2 + 9^4}{-6^0 + 2^0 - 8^1 + 9^1} \\
 6265 := \frac{6^3 + 2^{15} + 6^5 + 5^6}{6^0 + 2^0 + 6^1 + 5^0} & 6277 := \frac{6^7 + 2^{19} + 7^5 + 7^7}{6^2 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 7^2} & 6290 := \frac{-6^4 + 2^{10} + 9^4 + 0^0}{-6^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 0^1} \\
 6266 := \frac{6^2 + 2^{13} + 6^5 + 6^6}{6^0 + 2^1 + 6^0 + 6^1} & 6278 := \frac{-6^0 + 2^{10} - 7^4 + 8^5}{6^0 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 8^0} & 6291 := \frac{6^8 - 2^0 + 9^2 + 1^0}{6^0 + 2^8 + 9^1 + 1^0} \\
 6266 := \frac{6^2 + 2^{13} + 6^5 + 6^6}{6^0 + 2^1 + 6^0 + 6^1} & 6279 := \frac{6^2 + 2^{13} + 7^5 + 9^2}{6^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 9^0} & 6292 := \frac{6^0 - 2^{12} - 9^1 + 2^{20}}{6^2 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 2^7} \\
 6267 := \frac{6^5 - 2^{10} + 6^5 + 7^5}{6^0 + 2^1 + 6^0 + 7^0} & 6279 := \frac{6^2 + 2^{13} + 7^5 + 9^2}{6^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 9^0} & 6293 := \frac{6^0 + 2^{12} + 9^1 + 3^7}{6^0 - 2^1 + 9^0 + 3^0} \\
 6268 := \frac{6^6 + 2^{20} + 6^6 + 8^6}{6^1 + 2^0 + 6^3 + 8^0} & 6280 := \frac{-6^5 + 2^7 + 8^5 + 0^1}{6^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 0^0} & 6294 := \frac{-6^6 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 4^8}{-6^0 - 2^0 + 9^0 + 4^1} \\
 6268 := \frac{6^6 + 2^{20} + 6^6 + 8^6}{6^1 + 2^0 + 6^3 + 8^0} & 6282 := \frac{6^1 + 2^{19} + 8^3 + 2^{19}}{6^1 + 2^5 + 8^0 + 2^7} & 6295 := \frac{6^7 + 2^{19} + 9^8 + 5^2}{6^3 + 2^6 + 9^4 + 5^3}
 \end{array}$$

$$6295 := \frac{6^7 + 2^{19} + 9^8 + 5^2}{6^3 + 2^6 + 9^4 + 5^3}$$

$$6296 := \frac{-6^0 + 2^{16} + 9^1 - 6^6}{-6^0 - 2^0 - 9^0 + 6^1}$$

$$6297 := \frac{6^2 + 2^{17} + 9^6 + 7^7}{6^3 + 2^2 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$6297 := \frac{6^2 + 2^{17} + 9^6 + 7^7}{6^3 + 2^2 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$6298 := \frac{6^0 - 2^8 + 9^4 - 8^1}{6^0 + 2^0 - 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$6299 := \frac{6^3 + 2^{17} + 9^3 + 9^4}{6^1 - 2^1 + 9^1 + 9^1}$$

$$6302 := \frac{-6^6 + 3^3 - 0^0 + 2^{16}}{6^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 2^0}$$

$$6304 := \frac{-6^0 + 3^8 + 0^1 - 4^4}{-6^0 - 3^0 - 0^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6305 := \frac{6^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 5^6}{6^1 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 5^1}$$

$$6305 := \frac{6^6 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 5^6}{6^1 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 5^1}$$

$$6307 := \frac{6^7 - 3^3 + 0^1 - 7^4}{6^2 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 7^1}$$

$$6308 := \frac{6^8 + 3^{11} + 0^0 + 8^4}{-6^3 - 3^0 + 0^1 + 8^3}$$

$$6309 := \frac{6^7 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 9^9}{6^3 + 3^7 + 0^1 + 9^5}$$

$$6309 := \frac{6^7 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 9^9}{6^3 + 3^7 + 0^1 + 9^5}$$

$$6311 := \frac{6^7 - 3^{10} - 1^0 - 1^0}{6^1 + 3^3 + 1^0 + 1^0}$$

$$6312 := \frac{6^1 + 3^8 + 1^0 - 2^8}{-6^0 - 3^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6313 := \frac{-6^1 - 3^5 + 1^0 + 3^8}{6^1 - 3^0 - 1^0 - 3^1}$$

$$6314 := \frac{-6^1 + 3^{10} + 1^0 + 4^6}{-6^0 + 3^2 + 1^0 + 4^0}$$

$$6315 := \frac{6^6 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 5^5}{6^1 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$6315 := \frac{6^6 + 3^9 + 1^0 + 5^5}{6^1 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$6316 := \frac{-6^4 - 3^9 - 1^0 + 6^7}{6^0 + 3^1 + 1^0 + 6^2}$$

$$6317 := \frac{-6^6 + 3^{13} - 1^0 - 7^0}{6^3 + 3^3 + 1^0 + 7^0}$$

$$6318 := \frac{6^2 + 3^7 - 1^0 + 8^4}{6^0 - 3^2 + 1^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6319 := \frac{-6^3 - 3^3 + 1^0 + 9^4}{-6^1 - 3^0 - 1^0 + 9^1}$$

$$6320 := \frac{6^2 + 3^7 + 2^{12} + 0^0}{-6^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 0^1}$$

$$6321 := \frac{6^2 + 3^{12} - 2^9 - 1^0}{6^0 + 3^4 + 2^0 + 1^0}$$

$$6322 := \frac{6^4 + 3^{12} + 2^0 + 2^{17}}{6^1 + 3^1 + 2^5 + 2^6}$$

$$6322 := \frac{6^4 + 3^{12} + 2^0 + 2^{17}}{6^1 + 3^1 + 2^5 + 2^6}$$

$$6323 := \frac{6^9 + 3^6 + 2^7 + 3^{12}}{6^3 + 3^6 + 2^2 + 3^6}$$

$$6323 := \frac{6^9 + 3^6 + 2^7 + 3^{12}}{6^3 + 3^6 + 2^2 + 3^6}$$

$$6324 := \frac{6^3 + 3^{15} + 2^5 + 4^0}{6^3 + 3^0 + 2^{11} + 4^1}$$

$$6324 := \frac{6^3 + 3^{15} + 2^5 + 4^0}{6^3 + 3^0 + 2^{11} + 4^1}$$

$$6325 := \frac{6^0 + 3^1 + 2^{12} + 5^7}{6^0 + 3^1 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$6325 := \frac{6^0 + 3^1 + 2^{12} + 5^7}{6^0 + 3^1 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$6326 := \frac{6^0 + 3^5 + 2^{20} + 6^4}{6^0 + 3^0 + 2^7 + 6^2}$$

$$6326 := \frac{6^0 + 3^5 + 2^{20} + 6^4}{6^0 + 3^0 + 2^7 + 6^2}$$

$$6327 := \frac{6^2 + 3^{10} + 2^5 + 7^5}{6^0 + 3^1 + 2^0 + 7^1}$$

$$6327 := \frac{6^2 + 3^{10} + 2^5 + 7^5}{6^0 + 3^1 + 2^0 + 7^1}$$

$$6328 := \frac{-6^3 + 3^8 - 2^4 - 8^0}{-6^0 - 3^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$6329 := \frac{6^1 + 3^7 + 2^{11} + 9^5}{6^1 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$6329 := \frac{6^1 + 3^7 + 2^{11} + 9^5}{6^1 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$6330 := \frac{6^2 + 3^5 + 3^{12} + 0^1}{6^0 + 3^0 + 3^4 + 0^0}$$

$$6330 := \frac{6^2 + 3^5 + 3^{12} + 0^1}{6^0 + 3^0 + 3^4 + 0^0}$$

$$6332 := \frac{6^2 + 3^7 + 3^{10} + 2^{11}}{6^1 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6332 := \frac{6^2 + 3^7 + 3^{10} + 2^{11}}{6^1 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6333 := \frac{6^7 + 3^4 + 3^8 + 3^{13}}{6^3 + 3^3 + 3^3 + 3^3}$$

$$6333 := \frac{6^7 + 3^4 + 3^8 + 3^{13}}{6^3 + 3^3 + 3^3 + 3^3}$$

$$6334 := \frac{6^4 + 3^7 + 3^{12} + 4^{10}}{6^3 + 3^1 + 3^3 + 4^1}$$

$$6334 := \frac{6^4 + 3^7 + 3^{12} + 4^{10}}{6^3 + 3^1 + 3^3 + 4^1}$$

$$6335 := \frac{6^1 + 3^8 + 3^{11} + 5^0}{6^1 + 3^2 + 3^2 + 5^1}$$

$$6335 := \frac{6^1 + 3^8 + 3^{11} + 5^0}{6^1 + 3^2 + 3^2 + 5^1}$$

$$6336 := \frac{6^2 + 3^2 + 3^{13} + 6^6}{6^0 + 3^2 + 3^5 + 6^1}$$

$$6336 := \frac{6^2 + 3^2 + 3^{13} + 6^6}{6^0 + 3^2 + 3^5 + 6^1}$$

$$6337 := \frac{6^4 + 3^6 + 3^6 + 7^6}{6^1 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 7^1}$$

$6337 := \frac{6^4 + 3^6 + 3^6 + 7^6}{6^1 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 7^1}$	$6349 := \frac{-6^3 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 9^4}{-6^0 - 3^0 + 4^1 - 9^0}$	$6362 := \frac{6^0 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 2^4}{-6^0 - 3^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$
$6338 := \frac{6^8 + 3^2 + 3^7 + 8^4}{6^1 + 3^2 + 3^5 + 8^1}$	$6350 := \frac{-6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 0^1}{-6^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$	$6362 := \frac{6^0 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 2^4}{-6^0 - 3^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$
$6338 := \frac{6^8 + 3^2 + 3^7 + 8^4}{6^1 + 3^2 + 3^5 + 8^1}$	$6351 := \frac{-6^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 1^0}{-6^1 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 1^0}$	$6363 := \frac{6^1 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 3^3}{6^1 + 3^0 + 6^2 + 3^0}$
$6339 := \frac{6^6 + 3^3 + 3^9 + 9^7}{6^1 + 3^1 + 3^3 + 9^3}$	$6352 := \frac{6^3 + 3^7 + 5^7 + 2^{11}}{6^0 + 3^1 + 5^0 + 2^3}$	$6363 := \frac{6^1 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 3^3}{6^1 + 3^0 + 6^2 + 3^0}$
$6339 := \frac{6^6 + 3^3 + 3^9 + 9^7}{6^1 + 3^1 + 3^3 + 9^3}$	$6352 := \frac{6^3 + 3^7 + 5^7 + 2^{11}}{6^0 + 3^1 + 5^0 + 2^3}$	$6364 := \frac{-6^6 + 3^7 + 6^7 + 4^0}{6^1 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 4^2}$
$6340 := \frac{6^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 0^0}{-6^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$	$6353 := \frac{6^7 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 3^{11}}{6^2 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 3^2}$	$6365 := \frac{6^7 + 3^5 + 6^7 + 5^1}{6^0 + 3^4 + 6^0 + 5^1}$
$6341 := \frac{-6^5 - 3^6 + 4^9 + 1^0}{6^2 - 3^0 + 4^1 + 1^0}$	$6353 := \frac{6^7 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 3^{11}}{6^2 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 3^2}$	$6365 := \frac{6^7 + 3^5 + 6^7 + 5^1}{6^0 + 3^4 + 6^0 + 5^1}$
$6342 := \frac{6^6 + 3^{16} + 4^0 + 2^9}{6^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 2^1}$	$6354 := \frac{6^6 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 4^5}{6^0 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 4^0}$	$6367 := \frac{6^7 + 3^4 + 6^7 + 7^3}{6^1 + 3^3 + 6^1 + 7^2}$
$6342 := \frac{6^6 + 3^{16} + 4^0 + 2^9}{6^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 2^1}$	$6354 := \frac{6^6 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 4^5}{6^0 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 4^0}$	$6367 := \frac{6^7 + 3^4 + 6^7 + 7^3}{6^1 + 3^3 + 6^1 + 7^2}$
$6343 := \frac{6^8 + 3^{10} + 4^7 + 3^{10}}{6^2 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 3^5}$	$6355 := \frac{6^8 + 3^6 + 5^7 + 5^7}{6^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 5^3}$	$6368 := \frac{-6^0 + 3^8 + 6^6 + 8^4}{6^0 + 3^0 + 6^1 + 8^0}$
$6343 := \frac{6^8 + 3^{10} + 4^7 + 3^{10}}{6^2 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 3^5}$	$6355 := \frac{6^8 + 3^6 + 5^7 + 5^7}{6^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 5^3}$	$6369 := \frac{6^3 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 9^2}{6^1 + 3^0 + 6^2 + 9^0}$
$6344 := \frac{6^6 - 3^0 + 4^0 + 4^6}{-6^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 4^1}$	$6356 := \frac{6^1 + 3^8 + 5^1 - 6^3}{-6^0 + 3^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$	$6369 := \frac{6^3 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 9^2}{6^1 + 3^0 + 6^2 + 9^0}$
$6345 := \frac{6^6 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^1}{6^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 5^1}$	$6356 := \frac{6^1 + 3^8 + 5^1 - 6^3}{-6^0 + 3^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$	$6370 := \frac{6^7 + 3^0 + 7^3 + 0^1}{6^2 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 0^1}$
$6345 := \frac{6^6 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^1}{6^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 5^1}$	$6357 := \frac{6^1 + 3^1 + 5^5 + 7^6}{6^1 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 7^1}$	$6370 := \frac{6^7 + 3^0 + 7^3 + 0^1}{6^2 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 0^1}$
$6346 := \frac{-6^0 - 3^9 + 4^8 - 6^5}{6^0 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 6^0}$	$6357 := \frac{6^1 + 3^1 + 5^5 + 7^6}{6^1 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 7^1}$	$6372 := \frac{6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8}{6^0 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 2^0}$
$6347 := \frac{6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5}{6^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 7^1}$	$6358 := \frac{6^2 + 3^{11} + 5^7 + 8^7}{6^0 + 3^5 + 5^3 + 8^0}$	$6372 := \frac{6^6 + 3^0 + 7^5 + 2^8}{6^0 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 2^0}$
$6347 := \frac{6^6 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^5}{6^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 7^1}$	$6358 := \frac{6^2 + 3^{11} + 5^7 + 8^7}{6^0 + 3^5 + 5^3 + 8^0}$	$6373 := \frac{6^3 + 3^1 + 7^6 + 3^{14}}{6^1 + 3^3 + 7^1 + 3^6}$
$6348 := \frac{6^0 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 8^4}{-6^0 - 3^0 + 4^1 - 8^0}$	$6359 := \frac{6^2 - 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^4}{-6^1 - 3^0 - 5^0 + 9^1}$	$6373 := \frac{6^3 + 3^1 + 7^6 + 3^{14}}{6^1 + 3^3 + 7^1 + 3^6}$

$$6374 := \frac{6^2 + 3^0 + 7^5 - 4^6}{-6^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$6375 := \frac{6^7 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 5^1}{6^1 + 3^2 + 7^1 + 5^2}$$

$$6375 := \frac{6^7 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 5^1}{6^1 + 3^2 + 7^1 + 5^2}$$

$$6376 := \frac{6^3 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6}{6^0 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$6376 := \frac{6^3 + 3^4 + 7^5 + 6^6}{6^0 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$6377 := \frac{-6^3 + 3^9 + 7^1 - 7^3}{6^1 - 3^0 - 7^0 - 7^0}$$

$$6378 := \frac{6^7 + 3^8 + 7^0 + 8^3}{6^2 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 8^0}$$

$$6378 := \frac{6^7 + 3^8 + 7^0 + 8^3}{6^2 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 8^0}$$

$$6379 := \frac{6^4 + 3^{11} + 7^8 + 9^6}{6^2 + 3^5 + 7^1 + 9^3}$$

$$6379 := \frac{6^4 + 3^{11} + 7^8 + 9^6}{6^2 + 3^5 + 7^1 + 9^3}$$

$$6380 := \frac{6^6 + 3^{15} + 8^4 + 0^0}{6^1 + 3^7 + 8^2 + 0^1}$$

$$6380 := \frac{6^6 + 3^{15} + 8^4 + 0^0}{6^1 + 3^7 + 8^2 + 0^1}$$

$$6381 := \frac{-6^4 + 3^{12} - 8^6 + 1^0}{6^1 + 3^3 + 8^1 + 1^0}$$

$$6382 := \frac{6^7 + 3^{13} + 8^0 + 2^{11}}{6^2 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 2^8}$$

$$6382 := \frac{6^7 + 3^{13} + 8^0 + 2^{11}}{6^2 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 2^8}$$

$$6383 := \frac{6^8 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 3^{11}}{6^3 + 3^1 + 8^2 + 3^2}$$

$$6383 := \frac{6^8 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 3^{11}}{6^3 + 3^1 + 8^2 + 3^2}$$

$$6384 := \frac{-6^0 + 3^8 + 8^5 - 4^5}{6^0 + 3^1 + 8^0 + 4^0}$$

$$6385 := \frac{6^8 + 3^3 + 8^7 + 5^5}{6^3 + 3^5 + 8^1 + 5^3}$$

$$6385 := \frac{6^8 + 3^3 + 8^7 + 5^5}{6^3 + 3^5 + 8^1 + 5^3}$$

$$6386 := \frac{6^0 + 3^6 + 8^6 + 6^7}{6^1 + 3^2 + 8^2 + 6^1}$$

$$6386 := \frac{6^0 + 3^6 + 8^6 + 6^7}{6^1 + 3^2 + 8^2 + 6^1}$$

$$6387 := \frac{6^2 + 3^3 - 8^4 + 7^5}{-6^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$6388 := \frac{6^0 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 8^3}{-6^0 - 3^1 - 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6389 := \frac{6^7 - 3^7 + 8^4 - 9^3}{6^1 - 3^3 + 8^2 + 9^0}$$

$$6390 := \frac{6^3 + 3^9 - 9^3 + 0^1}{6^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 0^1}$$

$$6392 := \frac{6^2 + 3^9 + 9^7 + 2^{12}}{6^1 + 3^0 + 9^3 + 2^4}$$

$$6392 := \frac{6^2 + 3^9 + 9^7 + 2^{12}}{6^1 + 3^0 + 9^3 + 2^4}$$

$$6393 := \frac{6^8 + 3^2 + 9^3 + 3^{14}}{6^2 + 3^1 + 9^3 + 3^5}$$

$$6393 := \frac{6^8 + 3^2 + 9^3 + 3^{14}}{6^2 + 3^1 + 9^3 + 3^5}$$

$$6394 := \frac{6^1 + 3^1 + 9^0 + 4^9}{6^0 + 3^3 + 9^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6394 := \frac{6^1 + 3^1 + 9^0 + 4^9}{6^0 + 3^3 + 9^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6395 := \frac{6^8 + 3^7 + 9^2 + 5^0}{6^1 + 3^5 + 9^1 + 5^1}$$

$$6395 := \frac{6^8 + 3^7 + 9^2 + 5^0}{6^1 + 3^5 + 9^1 + 5^1}$$

$$6396 := \frac{-6^4 - 3^1 - 9^2 + 6^5}{-6^0 - 3^0 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$6397 := \frac{6^2 + 3^{13} + 9^4 + 7^7}{6^1 + 3^5 + 9^2 + 7^2}$$

$$6397 := \frac{6^2 + 3^{13} + 9^4 + 7^7}{6^1 + 3^5 + 9^2 + 7^2}$$

$$6398 := \frac{-6^4 - 3^8 + 9^5 - 8^1}{-6^0 - 3^0 + 9^1 + 8^0}$$

$$6399 := \frac{6^4 + 3^7 + 9^5 + 9^5}{6^1 + 3^1 + 9^0 + 9^1}$$

$$6399 := \frac{6^4 + 3^7 + 9^5 + 9^5}{6^1 + 3^1 + 9^0 + 9^1}$$

$$6403 := \frac{6^1 + 4^0 + 0^0 + 3^{12}}{6^0 + 4^0 + 0^1 + 3^4}$$

$$6403 := \frac{6^1 + 4^0 + 0^0 + 3^{12}}{6^0 + 4^0 + 0^1 + 3^4}$$

$$6405 := \frac{-6^7 + 4^{12} + 0^1 - 5^{10}}{6^0 + 4^5 + 0^0 + 5^2}$$

$$6407 := \frac{6^9 - 4^7 + 0^0 - 7^6}{6^4 + 4^4 - 0^0 + 7^0}$$

$$6408 := \frac{6^6 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 8^3}{6^1 + 4^0 + 0^1 + 8^0}$$

$$6408 := \frac{6^6 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 8^3}{6^1 + 4^0 + 0^1 + 8^0}$$

$$6409 := \frac{6^8 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 9^7}{6^3 + 4^3 + 0^3 + 9^3}$$

$$6409 := \frac{6^8 + 4^6 + 0^1 + 9^7}{6^3 + 4^3 + 0^3 + 9^3}$$

$$6411 := \frac{6^8 + 4^3 + 1^0 + 1^0}{6^1 + 4^4 - 1^0 + 1^0}$$

$$6413 := \frac{6^7 + 4^9 - 1^0 + 3^{15}}{6^4 + 4^5 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$6416 := \frac{-6^0 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 6^8}{-6^0 - 4^5 + 1^0 + 6^4}$$

$$6418 := \frac{-6^5 + 4^8 + 1^0 + 8^0}{6^1 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 8^0}$$

$$6420 := \frac{6^2 + 4^{10} + 2^{19} + 0^1}{-6^1 - 4^1 + 2^8 - 0^0}$$

$$6422 := \frac{6^1 + 4^5 + 2^7 + 2^{18}}{6^0 + 4^1 + 2^2 + 2^5}$$

$$6422 := \frac{6^1 + 4^5 + 2^7 + 2^{18}}{6^0 + 4^1 + 2^2 + 2^5}$$

$$6423 := \frac{6^7 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 3^{10}}{6^1 + 4^2 + 2^5 + 3^2}$$

$$6423 := \frac{6^7 + 4^8 + 2^7 + 3^{10}}{6^1 + 4^2 + 2^5 + 3^2}$$

$$6424 := \frac{6^5 + 4^5 + 2^9 + 4^7}{6^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$6425 := \frac{6^4 + 4^6 + 2^3 + 5^7}{6^1 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 5^1}$$

$$6425 := \frac{6^4 + 4^6 + 2^3 + 5^7}{6^1 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 5^1}$$

$$6426 := \frac{6^3 + 4^{12} + 2^{15} + 6^3}{6^4 + 4^2 + 2^3 + 6^4}$$

$$6426 := \frac{6^3 + 4^{12} + 2^{15} + 6^3}{6^4 + 4^2 + 2^3 + 6^4}$$

$$6427 := \frac{6^7 + 4^4 + 2^{15} + 7^6}{6^0 + 4^0 + 2^4 + 7^2}$$

$$6427 := \frac{6^7 + 4^4 + 2^{15} + 7^6}{6^0 + 4^0 + 2^4 + 7^2}$$

$$6428 := \frac{6^6 - 4^5 - 2^3 - 8^5}{-6^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$6429 := \frac{6^0 + 4^4 + 2^{18} + 9^5}{6^0 + 4^2 + 2^5 + 9^0}$$

$$6429 := \frac{6^0 + 4^4 + 2^{18} + 9^5}{6^0 + 4^2 + 2^5 + 9^0}$$

$$6432 := \frac{-6^0 - 4^3 + 3^8 - 2^6}{-6^0 - 4^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6433 := \frac{6^2 + 4^5 + 3^0 + 3^{13}}{6^0 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 3^5}$$

$$6433 := \frac{6^2 + 4^5 + 3^0 + 3^{13}}{6^0 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 3^5}$$

$$6434 := \frac{6^0 - 4^3 + 3^8 - 4^3}{-6^0 - 4^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6435 := \frac{6^4 + 4^4 + 3^{13} + 5^1}{6^3 + 4^1 + 3^1 + 5^2}$$

$$6435 := \frac{6^4 + 4^4 + 3^{13} + 5^1}{6^3 + 4^1 + 3^1 + 5^2}$$

$$6436 := \frac{6^3 - 4^0 + 3^{10} - 6^5}{-6^0 - 4^0 + 3^2 + 6^0}$$

$$6437 := \frac{-6^0 + 4^8 - 3^{10} - 7^2}{-6^0 + 4^1 - 3^0 - 7^0}$$

$$6438 := \frac{6^8 + 4^0 + 3^8 + 8^5}{6^0 + 4^4 + 3^2 + 8^0}$$

$$6438 := \frac{6^8 + 4^0 + 3^8 + 8^5}{6^0 + 4^4 + 3^2 + 8^0}$$

$$6439 := \frac{-6^5 - 4^1 + 3^5 + 9^5}{-6^0 - 4^0 + 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$6442 := \frac{6^7 + 4^1 + 4^7 + 2^3}{6^1 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 2^5}$$

$$6442 := \frac{6^7 + 4^1 + 4^7 + 2^3}{6^1 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 2^5}$$

$$6443 := \frac{6^4 + 4^5 + 4^6 + 3^3}{-6^0 - 4^0 + 4^1 - 3^0}$$

$$6444 := \frac{6^6 + 4^4 + 4^4 + 4^9}{6^2 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6444 := \frac{6^6 + 4^4 + 4^4 + 4^9}{6^2 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6445 := \frac{6^9 - 4^3 - 4^6 - 5^0}{6^4 + 4^2 + 4^4 - 5^1}$$

$$6446 := \frac{-6^2 + 4^4 + 4^8 - 6^4}{6^0 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 6^0}$$

$$6447 := \frac{6^2 + 4^4 + 4^{11} + 7^4}{6^2 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 7^3}$$

$$6447 := \frac{6^2 + 4^4 + 4^{11} + 7^4}{6^2 + 4^2 + 4^4 + 7^3}$$

$$6448 := \frac{-6^4 - 4^4 + 4^5 + 8^5}{-6^0 - 4^0 - 4^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6449 := \frac{6^6 - 4^4 + 4^9 + 9^5}{6^2 + 4^1 + 4^2 + 9^0}$$

$$6451 := \frac{6^{10} - 4^7 + 5^{12} - 1^0}{6^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 - 1^0}$$

$$6452 := \frac{6^4 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 2^{17}}{-6^0 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 2^4}$$

$$6453 := \frac{6^0 + 4^8 + 5^6 + 3^{17}}{6^3 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 3^9}$$

$$6453 := \frac{6^0 + 4^8 + 5^6 + 3^{17}}{6^3 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 3^9}$$

$$6454 := \frac{6^9 + 4^0 + 5^2 - 4^{10}}{-6^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 4^5}$$

$$6455 := \frac{6^8 + 4^{11} + 5^1 + 5^3}{6^3 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 5^4}$$

$$6455 := \frac{6^8 + 4^{11} + 5^1 + 5^3}{6^3 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 5^4}$$

$$6456 := \frac{-6^4 + 4^0 - 5^2 + 6^5}{-6^0 + 4^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$6457 := \frac{6^7 + 4^8 + 5^8 + 7^0}{6^2 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^2}$$

$$6457 := \frac{6^7 + 4^8 + 5^8 + 7^0}{6^2 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^2}$$

$$6458 := \frac{-6^0 + 4^7 + 5^7 - 8^4}{6^0 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6459 := \frac{6^7 + 4^5 + 5^9 + 9^3}{6^3 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^0}$$

$$6459 := \frac{6^7 + 4^5 + 5^9 + 9^3}{6^3 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^0}$$

$$6460 := \frac{-6^0 - 4^2 + 6^8 + 0^0}{-6^0 + 4^4 + 6^1 - 0^0}$$

$$6462 := \frac{6^3 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 2^9}{6^1 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 2^3}$$

$$6462 := \frac{6^3 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 2^9}{6^1 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 2^3}$$

$$6463 := \frac{6^6 + 4^9 + 6^6 + 3^2}{6^1 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 3^2}$$

$$6463 := \frac{6^6 + 4^9 + 6^6 + 3^2}{6^1 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 3^2}$$

$$6464 := \frac{6^5 - 4^4 + 6^5 + 4^6}{-6^0 - 4^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6465 := \frac{-6^4 - 4^2 + 6^5 + 5^0}{6^0 + 4^0 - 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$6467 := \frac{6^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4}{-6^0 + 4^0 - 6^1 + 7^1}$$

$$6467 := \frac{6^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4}{-6^0 + 4^0 - 6^1 + 7^1}$$

$$6468 := \frac{-6^4 - 4^1 + 6^5 - 8^1}{-6^0 + 4^1 - 6^0 - 8^0}$$

$$6469 := \frac{6^5 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 9^1}{6^1 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$6469 := \frac{6^5 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 9^1}{6^1 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$6470 := \frac{6^6 - 4^5 - 7^3 + 0^0}{6^0 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 0^0}$$

$$6471 := \frac{6^9 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 1^0}{6^4 + 4^4 + 7^1 + 1^0}$$

$$6471 := \frac{6^9 + 4^4 + 7^5 + 1^0}{6^4 + 4^4 + 7^1 + 1^0}$$

$$6472 := \frac{-6^0 - 4^3 - 7^3 + 2^{15}}{6^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6473 := \frac{6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5}{6^0 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 3^0}$$

$$6473 := \frac{6^6 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 3^5}{6^0 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 3^0}$$

$$6475 := \frac{6^5 - 4^9 + 7^7 + 5^4}{6^1 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 5^2}$$

$$6476 := \frac{6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6}{6^0 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$6476 := \frac{6^4 + 4^0 + 7^5 + 6^6}{6^0 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$6477 := \frac{6^6 + 4^6 + 7^0 + 7^6}{-6^1 - 4^2 - 7^0 + 7^2}$$

$$6478 := \frac{-6^2 + 4^0 - 7^3 + 8^5}{-6^0 - 4^0 - 7^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6479 := \frac{-6^0 + 4^8 - 7^1 - 9^5}{-6^0 + 4^1 - 7^0 - 9^0}$$

$$6482 := \frac{6^4 - 4^3 - 8^4 + 2^{18}}{6^1 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 2^5}$$

$$6483 := \frac{6^6 + 4^{12} + 8^1 + 3^{13}}{6^4 + 4^5 + 8^3 + 3^2}$$

$$6483 := \frac{6^6 + 4^{12} + 8^1 + 3^{13}}{6^4 + 4^5 + 8^3 + 3^2}$$

$$6484 := \frac{6^4 + 4^2 - 8^4 + 4^9}{6^2 - 4^0 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6485 := \frac{-6^6 - 4^4 - 8^1 + 5^8}{6^2 + 4^1 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$6486 := \frac{6^0 + 4^4 + 8^0 + 6^8}{6^0 + 4^4 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$6486 := \frac{6^0 + 4^4 + 8^0 + 6^8}{6^0 + 4^4 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$6487 := \frac{6^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 + 7^0}{6^0 + 4^4 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$6487 := \frac{6^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 + 7^0}{6^0 + 4^4 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$6488 := \frac{6^3 + 4^5 + 8^6 + 8^6}{6^0 + 4^3 + 8^1 + 8^1}$$

$$6488 := \frac{6^3 + 4^5 + 8^6 + 8^6}{6^0 + 4^3 + 8^1 + 8^1}$$

$$6489 := \frac{6^6 + 4^6 + 8^3 + 9^5}{6^1 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 9^1}$$

$$6489 := \frac{6^6 + 4^6 + 8^3 + 9^5}{6^1 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 9^1}$$

$$6490 := \frac{-6^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 - 0^0}{-6^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 0^1}$$

$$6492 := \frac{-6^0 - 4^1 + 9^4 - 2^6}{-6^0 - 4^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6493 := \frac{6^7 + 4^{10} + 9^6 + 3^{13}}{6^3 + 4^3 + 9^1 + 3^5}$$

$$6493 := \frac{6^7 + 4^{10} + 9^6 + 3^{13}}{6^3 + 4^3 + 9^1 + 3^5}$$

$$6494 := \frac{6^0 - 4^1 + 9^4 - 4^3}{-6^0 - 4^0 - 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6495 := \frac{-6^0 - 4^3 + 9^4 - 5^0}{-6^0 + 4^1 - 9^0 - 5^0}$$

$$6496 := \frac{-6^0 - 4^3 + 9^6 + 6^4}{6^2 + 4^0 + 9^1 + 6^2}$$

$$6497 := \frac{6^0 - 4^2 + 9^4 - 7^2}{-6^0 + 4^1 - 9^0 - 7^0}$$

$$6498 := \frac{-6^3 + 4^0 - 9^4 + 8^5}{6^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$6499 := \frac{6^0 - 4^3 + 9^0 + 9^4}{-6^0 + 4^1 - 9^0 - 9^0}$$

$$6502 := \frac{-6^3 + 5^6 + 0^0 + 2^{12}}{6^0 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 2^0}$$

$$6506 := \frac{-6^4 + 5^2 + 0^0 + 6^5}{-6^0 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 6^0}$$

$$6508 := \frac{-6^2 + 5^7 - 0^0 + 8^1}{6^1 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 8^0}$$

$$6509 := \frac{-6^6 + 5^4 + 0^1 + 9^5}{-6^0 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 9^0}$$

$$6510 := \frac{-6^1 + 5^7 + 1^0 + 0^1}{6^1 + 5^1 + 1^1 + 0^1}$$

$$6511 := \frac{-6^7 + 5^8 - 1^0 - 1^0}{-6^1 + 5^2 - 1^0 - 1^0}$$

$$6512 := \frac{6^2 + 5^7 - 1^0 - 2^4}{6^1 + 5^0 + 1^0 + 2^2}$$

$$6513 := \frac{6^8 - 5^4 + 1^0 - 3^{13}}{6^1 + 5^1 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$6516 := \frac{-6^4 + 5^6 - 1^0 - 6^4}{-6^0 + 5^0 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$6519 := \frac{-6^2 - 5^1 - 1^0 + 9^4}{-6^1 - 5^0 - 1^0 + 9^1}$$

$$6520 := \frac{-6^4 + 5^4 + 2^{17} - 0^0}{6^1 + 5^1 + 2^3 + 0^0}$$

$$6521 := \frac{-6^3 - 5^5 + 2^{14} - 1^0}{-6^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 1^0}$$

$$6522 := \frac{-6^3 - 5^5 + 2^0 + 2^{14}}{-6^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 6523 := \frac{6^1 + 5^7 + 2^6 + 3^4}{6^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 3^2} & 6533 := \frac{6^0 + 5^7 + 3^3 + 3^5}{6^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 3^2} & 6544 := \frac{-6^5 + 5^8 - 4^0 - 4^7}{6^0 - 5^1 - 4^1 + 4^3} \\
 6523 := \frac{6^1 + 5^7 + 2^6 + 3^4}{6^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 3^2} & 6534 := \frac{6^2 + 5^7 + 3^5 + 4^1}{6^0 + 5^0 + 3^2 + 4^0} & 6545 := \frac{6^5 + 5^6 + 4^3 + 5^9}{6^2 + 5^1 + 4^4 + 5^1} \\
 6524 := \frac{6^0 + 5^4 + 2^1 + 4^{11}}{6^0 + 5^4 + 2^0 + 4^2} & 6534 := \frac{6^2 + 5^7 + 3^5 + 4^1}{6^0 + 5^0 + 3^2 + 4^0} & 6545 := \frac{6^5 + 5^6 + 4^3 + 5^9}{6^2 + 5^1 + 4^4 + 5^1} \\
 6524 := \frac{6^0 + 5^4 + 2^1 + 4^{11}}{6^0 + 5^4 + 2^0 + 4^2} & 6535 := \frac{6^3 + 5^0 + 3^9 + 5^7}{6^1 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 5^1} & 6546 := \frac{-6^3 + 5^{11} + 4^0 - 6^4}{-6^2 - 5^2 - 4^4 + 6^5} \\
 6525 := \frac{6^5 + 5^2 + 2^{10} + 5^{10}}{6^3 + 5^4 + 2^5 + 5^4} & 6535 := \frac{6^3 + 5^0 + 3^9 + 5^7}{6^1 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 5^1} & 6547 := \frac{6^1 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 7^6}{6^0 + 5^2 + 4^0 + 7^0} \\
 6525 := \frac{6^5 + 5^2 + 2^{10} + 5^{10}}{6^3 + 5^4 + 2^5 + 5^4} & 6536 := \frac{6^2 + 5^2 + 3^9 + 6^8}{6^1 + 5^1 + 3^5 + 6^1} & 6547 := \frac{6^1 + 5^3 + 4^8 + 7^6}{6^0 + 5^2 + 4^0 + 7^0} \\
 6526 := \frac{6^0 - 5^1 + 2^{12} + 6^8}{6^0 + 5^2 + 2^4 + 6^3} & 6536 := \frac{6^2 + 5^2 + 3^9 + 6^8}{6^1 + 5^1 + 3^5 + 6^1} & 6548 := \frac{6^0 - 5^2 - 4^1 + 8^5}{-6^0 - 5^0 - 4^0 + 8^1} \\
 6527 := \frac{6^5 - 5^6 + 2^{12} + 7^5}{-6^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 7^0} & 6537 := \frac{6^8 + 5^7 + 3^6 + 7^6}{6^2 + 5^0 + 3^5 + 7^1} & 6549 := \frac{-6^0 + 5^1 - 4^2 + 9^4}{-6^0 - 5^0 + 4^1 - 9^0} \\
 6528 := \frac{-6^0 + 5^0 - 2^7 + 8^5}{6^0 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 8^0} & 6537 := \frac{6^8 + 5^7 + 3^6 + 7^6}{6^2 + 5^0 + 3^5 + 7^1} & 6552 := \frac{-6^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 2^{15}}{6^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 2^1} \\
 6529 := \frac{6^5 + 5^6 + 2^{15} + 9^6}{6^1 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 9^2} & 6538 := \frac{6^0 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 8^0}{6^0 + 5^0 - 3^2 + 8^1} & 6553 := \frac{-6^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 3^8}{6^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 - 3^1} \\
 6529 := \frac{6^5 + 5^6 + 2^{15} + 9^6}{6^1 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 9^2} & 6538 := \frac{6^0 - 5^2 + 3^8 + 8^0}{6^0 + 5^0 - 3^2 + 8^1} & 6554 := \frac{6^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 4^9}{6^1 + 5^1 + 5^2 + 4^1} \\
 6530 := \frac{6^7 + 5^3 + 3^6 + 0^1}{6^2 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 0^0} & 6539 := \frac{6^7 + 5^4 + 3^{11} + 9^4}{6^2 + 5^2 + 3^0 + 9^1} & 6554 := \frac{6^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 4^9}{6^1 + 5^1 + 5^2 + 4^1} \\
 6530 := \frac{6^7 + 5^3 + 3^6 + 0^1}{6^2 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 0^0} & 6539 := \frac{6^7 + 5^4 + 3^{11} + 9^4}{6^2 + 5^2 + 3^0 + 9^1} & 6556 := \frac{6^1 + 5^6 + 5^7 + 6^7}{6^0 + 5^2 + 5^2 + 6^1} \\
 6531 := \frac{6^3 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 1^0}{6^1 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 1^0} & 6541 := \frac{6^{10} + 5^4 + 4^{13} - 1^0}{-6^1 + 5^5 + 4^7 + 1^0} & 6556 := \frac{6^1 + 5^6 + 5^7 + 6^7}{6^0 + 5^2 + 5^2 + 6^1} \\
 6531 := \frac{6^3 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 1^0}{6^1 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 1^0} & 6542 := \frac{6^0 + 5^5 + 4^7 + 2^{16}}{6^1 + 5^0 + 4^1 + 2^1} & 6557 := \frac{-6^2 + 5^5 + 5^5 + 7^3}{-6^1 - 5^0 + 5^0 + 7^1} \\
 6532 := \frac{6^3 + 5^7 + 3^3 + 2^4}{6^0 + 5^0 + 3^2 + 2^0} & 6542 := \frac{6^0 + 5^5 + 4^7 + 2^{16}}{6^1 + 5^0 + 4^1 + 2^1} & 6558 := \frac{6^5 - 5^4 + 5^7 + 8^5}{-6^0 - 5^1 + 5^2 - 8^0} \\
 6532 := \frac{6^3 + 5^7 + 3^3 + 2^4}{6^0 + 5^0 + 3^2 + 2^0} & 6543 := \frac{6^7 + 5^7 + 4^{10} + 3^{15}}{6^3 + 5^0 + 4^1 + 3^7} & 6559 := \frac{-6^1 - 5^0 + 5^1 + 9^4}{-6^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 9^1} \\
 6533 := \frac{6^0 + 5^7 + 3^3 + 3^5}{6^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 3^2} & 6543 := \frac{6^7 + 5^7 + 4^{10} + 3^{15}}{6^3 + 5^0 + 4^1 + 3^7} & 6561 := \frac{-6^1 + 5^1 + 6^8 + 1^0}{6^2 + 5^1 + 6^3 - 1^0}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 6562 := \frac{6^0 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 2^{15}}{6^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 2^1} & 6576 := \frac{-6^2 + 5^6 - 7^4 - 6^2}{-6^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 6^0} & 6591 := \frac{6^1 + 5^2 + 9^4 - 1^0}{-6^1 - 5^0 + 9^1 - 1^0} \\
 6562 := \frac{6^0 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 2^{15}}{6^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 2^1} & 6577 := \frac{6^6 - 5^4 + 7^0 + 7^1}{6^1 - 5^0 + 7^0 + 7^0} & 6592 := \frac{-6^1 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 2^5}{-6^0 - 5^0 + 9^0 + 2^1} \\
 6563 := \frac{6^0 - 5^1 + 6^1 + 3^8}{-6^0 - 5^0 + 6^1 - 3^1} & 6578 := \frac{6^7 + 5^1 + 7^4 + 8^3}{6^2 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 8^0} & 6593 := \frac{6^4 + 5^{10} + 9^6 + 3^9}{6^4 + 5^2 + 9^0 + 3^5} \\
 6564 := \frac{-6^0 + 5^7 + 6^6 - 4^3}{6^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 4^2} & 6578 := \frac{6^7 + 5^1 + 7^4 + 8^3}{6^2 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 8^0} & 6594 := \frac{6^2 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 4^4}{6^1 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 4^0} \\
 6565 := \frac{-6^1 + 5^4 + 6^2 + 5^7}{6^0 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 5^1} & 6579 := \frac{6^2 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 9^5}{6^1 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 9^0} & 6594 := \frac{6^2 + 5^1 + 9^5 + 4^4}{6^1 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 4^0} \\
 6567 := \frac{6^3 + 5^3 + 6^3 + 7^6}{6^1 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 7^0} & 6580 := \frac{6^1 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 0^0}{-6^0 - 5^0 + 8^1 - 0^0} & 6595 := \frac{6^4 + 5^2 + 9^5 + 5^7}{6^1 + 5^0 + 9^1 + 5^1} \\
 6567 := \frac{6^3 + 5^3 + 6^3 + 7^6}{6^1 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 7^0} & 6581 := \frac{6^4 + 5^9 - 8^5 - 1^0}{-6^3 - 5^1 + 8^3 + 1^0} & 6595 := \frac{6^4 + 5^2 + 9^5 + 5^7}{6^1 + 5^0 + 9^1 + 5^1} \\
 6568 := \frac{-6^3 + 5^{10} + 6^5 - 8^0}{6^3 - 5^2 + 6^4 + 8^0} & 6582 := \frac{6^0 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 2^4}{6^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 2^1} & 6596 := \frac{-6^1 + 5^1 + 9^4 + 6^2}{-6^0 - 5^0 + 9^1 - 6^1} \\
 6569 := \frac{6^0 + 5^0 + 6^1 + 9^4}{-6^0 - 5^0 - 6^1 + 9^1} & 6582 := \frac{6^0 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 2^4}{6^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 2^1} & 6597 := \frac{6^4 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 7^6}{6^1 + 5^1 + 9^1 + 7^1} \\
 6570 := \frac{6^6 + 5^7 + 7^2 + 0^1}{6^1 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 0^0} & 6583 := \frac{6^5 + 5^1 + 8^6 + 3^8}{6^1 + 5^0 + 8^1 + 3^3} & 6597 := \frac{6^4 + 5^3 + 9^5 + 7^6}{6^1 + 5^1 + 9^1 + 7^1} \\
 6570 := \frac{6^6 + 5^7 + 7^2 + 0^1}{6^1 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 0^0} & 6583 := \frac{6^5 + 5^1 + 8^6 + 3^8}{6^1 + 5^0 + 8^1 + 3^3} & 6598 := \frac{6^2 + 5^6 - 9^4 + 8^4}{-6^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 8^0} \\
 6572 := \frac{6^1 + 5^4 + 7^6 + 2^4}{6^1 + 5^0 + 7^1 + 2^2} & 6584 := \frac{6^5 + 5^2 - 8^0 + 4^9}{-6^0 + 5^2 + 8^0 + 4^2} & 6599 := \frac{6^3 + 5^3 + 9^0 + 9^5}{6^1 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 9^0} \\
 6572 := \frac{6^1 + 5^4 + 7^6 + 2^4}{6^1 + 5^0 + 7^1 + 2^2} & 6585 := \frac{6^1 + 5^4 + 8^6 + 5^4}{6^1 + 5^0 + 8^1 + 5^2} & 6603 := \frac{6^1 + 6^2 + 0^1 + 3^8}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 3^0} \\
 6573 := \frac{6^7 + 5^5 + 7^6 + 3^5}{6^1 + 5^1 + 7^2 + 3^0} & 6585 := \frac{6^1 + 5^4 + 8^6 + 5^4}{6^1 + 5^0 + 8^1 + 5^2} & 6605 := \frac{-6^4 + 6^5 + 0^1 + 5^3}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 5^0} \\
 6574 := \frac{6^2 + 5^5 + 7^6 + 4^6}{6^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 4^2} & 6586 := \frac{6^0 + 5^6 + 8^4 + 6^2}{-6^0 - 5^0 - 8^0 + 6^1} & 6609 := \frac{6^3 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 9^5}{6^0 + 6^1 + 0^0 + 9^0} \\
 6574 := \frac{6^2 + 5^5 + 7^6 + 4^6}{6^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 4^2} & 6587 := \frac{-6^0 - 5^7 - 8^0 + 7^6}{-6^0 - 5^0 + 8^0 + 7^1} & 6609 := \frac{6^3 + 6^3 + 0^1 + 9^5}{6^0 + 6^1 + 0^0 + 9^0} \\
 6575 := \frac{6^9 + 5^1 + 7^6 + 5^6}{6^4 + 5^3 + 7^1 + 5^3} & 6588 := \frac{6^4 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 8^7}{6^3 - 5^2 + 8^2 + 8^2} & 6613 := \frac{6^6 + 6^6 - 1^0 - 3^6}{6^1 + 6^1 + 1^0 + 3^0} \\
 6575 := \frac{6^9 + 5^1 + 7^6 + 5^6}{6^4 + 5^3 + 7^1 + 5^3} & 6589 := \frac{6^6 - 5^4 + 8^2 - 9^4}{-6^0 - 5^0 - 8^0 + 9^1} & 6613 := \frac{6^6 + 6^6 - 1^6 - 3^6}{6^1 + 6^1 - 1^1 + 3^1}
 \end{array}$$

$$6620 := \frac{6^7 + 6^8 - 2^5 + 0^1}{-6^0 - 6^3 + 2^9 + 0^0}$$

$$6622 := \frac{6^2 + 6^6 + 2^2 + 2^{15}}{6^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 2^3}$$

$$6622 := \frac{6^2 + 6^6 + 2^2 + 2^{15}}{6^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 2^3}$$

$$6623 := \frac{6^0 + 6^8 + 2^{10} + 3^{12}}{6^2 + 6^3 + 2^0 + 3^4}$$

$$6623 := \frac{6^0 + 6^8 + 2^{10} + 3^{12}}{6^2 + 6^3 + 2^0 + 3^4}$$

$$6624 := \frac{6^5 + 6^6 + 2^{11} + 4^7}{6^0 + 6^0 + 2^3 + 4^0}$$

$$6624 := \frac{6^5 + 6^6 + 2^{11} + 4^7}{6^0 + 6^0 + 2^3 + 4^0}$$

$$6625 := \frac{6^3 + 6^5 + 2^3 + 5^7}{6^0 + 6^1 + 2^0 + 5^1}$$

$$6625 := \frac{6^3 + 6^5 + 2^3 + 5^7}{6^0 + 6^1 + 2^0 + 5^1}$$

$$6626 := \frac{6^3 + 6^4 + 2^{15} - 6^5}{6^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$6627 := \frac{6^2 + 6^2 + 2^{13} + 7^6}{6^0 + 6^0 + 2^4 + 7^0}$$

$$6627 := \frac{6^2 + 6^2 + 2^{13} + 7^6}{6^0 + 6^0 + 2^4 + 7^0}$$

$$6628 := \frac{6^4 + 6^6 - 2^{13} + 8^1}{-6^0 + 6^0 - 2^1 + 8^1}$$

$$6629 := \frac{6^2 + 6^2 - 2^2 + 9^4}{-6^0 - 6^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$6632 := \frac{6^0 + 6^1 + 3^8 + 2^6}{-6^0 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6633 := \frac{6^3 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 3^9}{6^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 3^1}$$

$$6633 := \frac{6^3 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 3^9}{6^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 3^1}$$

$$6634 := \frac{6^2 + 6^2 + 3^8 + 4^0}{-6^0 - 6^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6635 := \frac{6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1}{6^0 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 5^1}$$

$$6635 := \frac{6^1 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 5^1}{6^0 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 5^1}$$

$$6637 := \frac{6^5 + 6^6 + 3^{12} + 7^6}{6^2 + 6^2 + 3^3 + 7^1}$$

$$6637 := \frac{6^5 + 6^6 + 3^{12} + 7^6}{6^2 + 6^2 + 3^3 + 7^1}$$

$$6638 := \frac{-6^3 + 6^6 + 3^3 - 8^0}{-6^0 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6639 := \frac{6^8 + 6^{10} + 3^5 + 9^9}{6^4 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 9^2}$$

$$6639 := \frac{6^8 + 6^{10} + 3^5 + 9^9}{6^4 + 6^6 + 3^9 + 9^2}$$

$$6642 := \frac{6^3 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 2^{15}}{6^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 2^2}$$

$$6642 := \frac{6^3 + 6^6 + 4^3 + 2^{15}}{6^0 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 2^2}$$

$$6643 := \frac{6^2 + 6^8 + 4^5 + 3^1}{6^1 + 6^3 + 4^1 + 3^3}$$

$$6643 := \frac{6^2 + 6^8 + 4^5 + 3^1}{6^1 + 6^3 + 4^1 + 3^3}$$

$$6644 := \frac{-6^3 + 6^6 + 4^1 + 4^3}{6^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6645 := \frac{-6^3 + 6^5 + 4^8 - 5^0}{6^0 + 6^0 + 4^1 + 5^1}$$

$$6647 := \frac{6^2 - 6^5 + 4^7 + 7^6}{6^0 + 6^0 + 4^2 + 7^0}$$

$$6648 := \frac{-6^5 + 6^6 - 4^7 + 8^4}{6^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$6649 := \frac{6^2 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 9^4}{-6^0 - 6^0 + 4^1 - 9^0}$$

$$6652 := \frac{-6^0 - 6^4 + 5^6 - 2^{10}}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$6653 := \frac{6^1 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 3^8}{6^0 + 6^0 + 5^1 + 3^0}$$

$$6653 := \frac{6^1 + 6^6 + 5^0 + 3^8}{6^0 + 6^0 + 5^1 + 3^0}$$

$$6654 := \frac{-6^2 + 6^9 - 5^9 - 4^0}{6^2 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 4^5}$$

$$6655 := \frac{-6^3 + 6^8 - 5^2 - 5^6}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 5^3 + 5^3}$$

$$6657 := \frac{6^1 + 6^7 - 5^1 - 7^3}{-6^0 - 6^0 - 5^1 + 7^2}$$

$$6658 := \frac{-6^0 - 6^1 + 5^3 + 8^7}{-6^1 - 6^3 + 5^2 + 8^3}$$

$$6659 := \frac{-6^3 + 6^5 + 5^7 - 9^5}{6^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$6660 := \frac{-6^0 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 0^0}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 0^0}$$

$$6661 := \frac{6^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 1^0}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 1^0}$$

$$6662 := \frac{6^1 - 6^2 + 6^6 + 2^3}{6^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 2^2}$$

$$6663 := \frac{6^3 + 6^7 + 6^{10} + 3^5}{6^2 + 6^4 + 6^5 + 3^2}$$

$$6663 := \frac{6^3 + 6^7 + 6^{10} + 3^5}{6^2 + 6^4 + 6^5 + 3^2}$$

$$6664 := \frac{-6^0 - 6^1 + 6^6 - 4^0}{6^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6665 := \frac{-6^0 - 6^0 + 6^6 + 5^0}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 5^0}$$

$$6666 := \frac{6^1 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 6^6}{6^0 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 6^1}$$

$$6666 := \frac{6^1 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 6^6}{6^0 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 6^1}$$

$$6667 := \frac{6^1 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 7^0}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 7^0}$$

$$6668 := \frac{6^1 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^1}{-6^0 - 6^0 + 6^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6669 := \frac{6^2 + 6^2 + 6^2 + 9^4}{-6^0 - 6^0 - 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$6670 := \frac{6^4 + 6^5 - 7^4 - 0^0}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 0^1}$$

$$6672 := \frac{6^4 + 6^5 - 7^4 + 2^0}{-6^0 - 6^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6673 := \frac{6^4 - 6^6 - 7^3 + 3^{10}}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$6674 := \frac{-6^0 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 4^3}{6^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6675 := \frac{6^5 + 6^6 + 7^7 + 5^5}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 5^3}$$

$$6676 := \frac{6^0 - 6^4 + 7^7 - 6^5}{6^0 + 6^2 + 7^2 + 6^2}$$

$$6677 := \frac{-6^3 + 6^{10} - 7^5 - 7^7}{-6^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 + 7^4}$$

$$6679 := \frac{6^3 + 6^6 - 7^0 + 9^4}{-6^0 - 6^0 + 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$6682 := \frac{-6^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 - 2^{10}}{-6^0 - 6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6683 := \frac{6^5 + 6^5 + 8^0 - 3^7}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$6684 := \frac{6^6 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 4^4}{6^0 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6684 := \frac{6^6 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 4^4}{6^0 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6685 := \frac{6^1 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 5^3}{-6^0 - 6^0 + 8^1 + 5^0}$$

$$6686 := \frac{-6^1 + 6^3 - 8^2 + 6^6}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$6687 := \frac{6^4 + 6^4 + 8^4 - 7^0}{6^0 + 6^0 - 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$6688 := \frac{6^3 + 6^6 + 8^1 - 8^2}{-6^0 - 6^0 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6689 := \frac{6^4 + 6^4 + 8^4 + 9^0}{-6^0 + 6^0 - 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$6692 := \frac{-6^0 - 6^2 + 9^3 + 2^{15}}{6^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6693 := \frac{6^{15} + 6^{20} + 9^{14} + 3^{19}}{6^{14} + 6^{15} + 9^8 + 3^{19}}$$

$$6693 := \frac{6^{15} + 6^{20} + 9^{14} + 3^{19}}{6^{14} + 6^{15} + 9^8 + 3^{19}}$$

$$6694 := \frac{-6^0 + 6^7 - 9^5 + 4^2}{-6^0 + 6^2 - 9^0 - 4^0}$$

$$6696 := \frac{-6^0 + 6^3 + 9^0 + 6^6}{-6^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 6^1}$$

$$6697 := \frac{-6^4 + 6^8 + 9^7 - 7^8}{-6^1 + 6^2 + 9^2 - 7^1}$$

$$6698 := \frac{-6^0 - 6^1 + 9^3 + 8^5}{-6^0 - 6^0 - 9^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6699 := \frac{-6^2 + 6^7 + 9^3 + 9^3}{6^1 + 6^2 - 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$6702 := \frac{6^6 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 2^8}{6^0 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 2^2}$$

$$6702 := \frac{6^6 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 2^8}{6^0 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 2^2}$$

$$6703 := \frac{6^5 - 7^3 - 0^0 - 3^6}{-6^0 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 3^0}$$

$$6704 := \frac{6^5 - 7^2 + 0^0 - 4^5}{-6^0 - 7^0 - 0^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6705 := \frac{6^4 + 7^7 + 0^0 - 5^3}{-6^0 - 7^0 + 0^1 + 5^3}$$

$$6707 := \frac{6^6 - 7^2 - 0^0 + 7^3}{-6^0 + 7^0 + 0^1 + 7^1}$$

$$6712 := \frac{6^3 + 7^4 - 1^0 + 2^{12}}{-6^0 - 7^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6713 := \frac{6^6 + 7^3 + 1^0 - 3^2}{6^1 - 7^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$6714 := \frac{6^3 + 7^4 + 1^0 + 4^6}{-6^0 - 7^0 - 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6715 := \frac{6^6 + 7^3 + 1^0 + 5^1}{6^1 - 7^0 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$6716 := \frac{6^6 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 6^9}{6^3 - 7^0 - 1^0 + 6^4}$$

$$6718 := \frac{6^{10} + 7^4 - 1^0 + 8^6}{-6^5 + 7^5 + 1^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6720 := \frac{6^3 - 7^3 + 2^{19} - 0^0}{6^1 + 7^1 + 2^6 + 0^0}$$

$$6722 := \frac{6^0 + 7^5 + 2^2 + 2^{17}}{6^0 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 2^4}$$

$$6722 := \frac{6^0 + 7^5 + 2^2 + 2^{17}}{6^0 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 2^4}$$

$$6723 := \frac{6^0 + 7^2 + 2^{18} + 3^1}{6^0 + 7^1 + 2^2 + 3^3}$$

$$6723 := \frac{6^0 + 7^2 + 2^{18} + 3^1}{6^0 + 7^1 + 2^2 + 3^3}$$

$$6724 := \frac{-6^0 - 7^3 + 2^{11} + 4^8}{6^0 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 4^1}$$

$$6725 := \frac{6^1 + 7^7 + 2^{20} + 5^7}{6^2 + 7^0 + 2^7 + 5^3}$$

$$6725 := \frac{6^1 + 7^7 + 2^{20} + 5^7}{6^2 + 7^0 + 2^7 + 5^3}$$

$$6726 := \frac{-6^0 - 7^6 + 2^{15} + 6^7}{6^1 + 7^0 + 2^4 + 6^1}$$

$$6727 := \frac{-6^0 - 7^5 + 2^6 + 7^6}{6^1 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 7^1}$$

$$6728 := \frac{6^3 + 7^6 + 2^{17} - 8^0}{6^1 + 7^1 + 2^4 + 8^1}$$

$$6729 := \frac{-6^0 - 7^3 + 2^9 + 9^4}{-6^0 - 7^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$6731 := \frac{-6^2 + 7^3 + 3^{12} + 1^0}{6^1 - 7^1 + 3^4 - 1^0}$$

$$6732 := \frac{6^3 + 7^5 + 3^2 + 2^{17}}{6^1 + 7^1 + 3^0 + 2^3}$$

$$6733 := \frac{6^3 + 7^1 + 3^5 + 3^{12}}{6^2 + 7^1 + 3^2 + 3^3}$$

$$6733 := \frac{6^3 + 7^1 + 3^5 + 3^{12}}{6^2 + 7^1 + 3^2 + 3^3}$$

$$6734 := \frac{-6^1 + 7^4 + 3^5 + 4^6}{-6^0 - 7^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 6735 := \frac{6^0 + 7^0 + 3^1 + 5^8}{6^0 + 7^2 + 3^1 + 5^1} & 6752 := \frac{6^4 + 7^5 + 5^6 + 2^5}{6^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 2^1} & 6768 := \frac{-6^4 + 7^6 - 6^4 - 8^0}{6^0 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 8^1} \\
 6735 := \frac{6^0 + 7^0 + 3^1 + 5^8}{6^0 + 7^2 + 3^1 + 5^1} & 6752 := \frac{6^4 + 7^5 + 5^6 + 2^5}{6^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 2^1} & 6769 := \frac{-6^0 - 7^1 + 6^3 + 9^4}{-6^0 - 7^0 - 6^1 + 9^1} \\
 6736 := \frac{6^8 + 7^5 + 3^{14} + 6^9}{6^1 + 7^2 + 3^7 + 6^3} & 6753 := \frac{6^3 + 7^0 - 5^2 + 3^8}{6^1 - 7^0 - 5^0 - 3^1} & 6772 := \frac{6^7 + 7^2 + 7^3 + 2^{12}}{6^2 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 2^2} \\
 6736 := \frac{6^8 + 7^5 + 3^{14} + 6^9}{6^1 + 7^2 + 3^7 + 6^3} & 6754 := \frac{6^5 + 7^0 + 5^0 - 4^5}{-6^0 - 7^0 - 5^0 + 4^1} & 6772 := \frac{6^7 + 7^2 + 7^3 + 2^{12}}{6^2 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 2^2} \\
 6737 := \frac{-6^3 + 7^2 + 3^8 + 7^3}{-6^1 - 7^0 + 3^0 + 7^1} & 6755 := \frac{6^6 - 7^0 + 5^1 + 5^4}{6^1 - 7^0 + 5^0 + 5^0} & 6773 := \frac{6^5 + 7^5 + 7^6 + 3^0}{6^1 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 3^0} \\
 6738 := \frac{6^2 + 7^5 + 3^6 - 8^4}{-6^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 8^0} & 6756 := \frac{-6^6 - 7^2 + 5^8 - 6^6}{6^1 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 6^2} & 6773 := \frac{6^5 + 7^5 + 7^6 + 3^0}{6^1 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 3^0} \\
 6739 := \frac{-6^2 + 7^4 - 3^7 + 9^4}{-6^1 - 7^0 - 3^0 + 9^1} & 6757 := \frac{6^5 - 7^0 - 5^7 + 7^6}{6^1 - 7^0 + 5^0 + 7^0} & 6774 := \frac{6^7 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 4^8}{6^2 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 4^0} \\
 6742 := \frac{-6^5 + 7^7 - 4^0 + 2^4}{6^1 + 7^2 + 4^3 + 2^1} & 6758 := \frac{6^7 + 7^6 + 5^4 + 8^3}{6^0 + 7^2 + 5^0 + 8^1} & 6774 := \frac{6^7 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 4^8}{6^2 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 4^0} \\
 6743 := \frac{6^4 + 7^3 - 4^0 + 3^{10}}{6^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 3^1} & 6758 := \frac{6^7 + 7^6 + 5^4 + 8^3}{6^0 + 7^2 + 5^0 + 8^1} & 6775 := \frac{6^{10} + 7^4 - 7^9 + 5^1}{6^5 - 7^4 - 7^4 - 5^1} \\
 6744 := \frac{6^5 - 7^1 - 4^0 - 4^5}{-6^0 - 7^0 - 4^0 + 4^1} & 6759 := \frac{6^8 + 7^5 + 5^1 + 9^2}{6^3 + 7^0 + 5^2 + 9^1} & 6776 := \frac{-6^1 + 7^3 - 7^6 + 6^7}{-6^1 + 7^0 - 7^1 + 6^2} \\
 6745 := \frac{6^2 + 7^{11} + 4^8 + 5^{10}}{6^2 + 7^5 + 4^9 + 5^6} & 6759 := \frac{6^8 + 7^5 + 5^1 + 9^2}{6^3 + 7^0 + 5^2 + 9^1} & 6778 := \frac{6^7 - 7^3 + 7^4 - 8^4}{-6^0 + 7^0 + 7^2 - 8^1} \\
 6745 := \frac{6^2 + 7^{11} + 4^8 + 5^{10}}{6^2 + 7^5 + 4^9 + 5^6} & 6761 := \frac{6^5 - 7^3 + 6^6 - 1^0}{-6^0 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 1^0} & 6779 := \frac{6^3 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 9^4}{-6^1 - 7^0 - 7^0 + 9^1} \\
 6746 := \frac{6^0 - 7^1 - 4^5 + 6^5}{-6^0 - 7^0 + 4^1 - 6^0} & 6762 := \frac{-6^0 - 7^6 + 6^7 + 2^1}{6^0 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 2^4} & 6782 := \frac{6^0 + 7^6 + 8^6 - 2^1}{-6^0 + 7^0 - 8^1 + 2^6} \\
 6747 := \frac{6^5 + 7^4 + 4^1 + 7^5}{6^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 7^0} & 6763 := \frac{-6^0 + 7^5 + 6^4 + 3^7}{-6^0 - 7^0 + 6^1 - 3^0} & 6783 := \frac{6^3 + 7^1 - 8^0 + 3^8}{-6^0 + 7^0 - 8^1 + 3^2} \\
 6747 := \frac{6^5 + 7^4 + 4^1 + 7^5}{6^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 7^0} & 6764 := \frac{6^0 + 7^6 + 6^1 + 4^6}{6^0 + 7^1 + 6^1 + 4^1} & 6784 := \frac{6^0 + 7^7 + 8^1 + 4^6}{6^0 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 4^3} \\
 6748 := \frac{6^5 - 7^0 + 4^0 + 8^6}{-6^0 - 7^1 - 4^2 + 8^2} & 6764 := \frac{6^0 + 7^6 + 6^1 + 4^6}{6^0 + 7^1 + 6^1 + 4^1} & 6784 := \frac{6^0 + 7^7 + 8^1 + 4^6}{6^0 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 4^3} \\
 6749 := \frac{6^7 - 7^5 + 4^0 + 9^2}{6^2 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 9^0} & 6765 := \frac{-6^1 + 7^5 - 6^3 + 5^7}{6^0 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 5^1} & 6785 := \frac{6^6 - 7^3 - 8^5 + 5^2}{-6^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 5^0} \\
 6751 := \frac{6^1 + 7^6 + 5^7 - 1^0}{6^1 - 7^0 + 5^2 - 1^0} & 6767 := \frac{-6^3 + 7^7 - 6^7 + 7^7}{-6^1 - 7^0 + 6^3 - 7^1} & 6786 := \frac{-6^4 + 7^6 - 8^0 - 6^5}{6^0 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 6^1}
 \end{array}$$

$$6787 := \frac{-6^6 - 7^5 + 8^2 + 7^7}{6^1 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 7^2}$$

$$6788 := \frac{6^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 + 8^8}{6^0 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 8^2}$$

$$6789 := \frac{6^2 + 7^7 - 8^6 - 9^5}{-6^0 - 7^1 + 8^0 + 9^2}$$

$$6792 := \frac{6^7 + 7^5 + 9^2 + 2^{17}}{6^0 + 7^2 + 9^1 + 2^2}$$

$$6793 := \frac{6^4 + 7^1 + 9^3 + 3^{13}}{6^3 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 3^2}$$

$$6794 := \frac{6^3 + 7^0 + 9^4 + 4^2}{-6^0 - 7^0 - 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6795 := \frac{6^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 + 5^2}{-6^1 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 5^1}$$

$$6796 := \frac{-6^0 + 7^6 + 9^5 - 6^0}{6^1 - 7^1 - 9^1 + 6^2}$$

$$6797 := \frac{6^4 - 7^4 - 9^0 + 7^7}{-6^3 - 7^1 + 9^0 + 7^3}$$

$$6798 := \frac{6^4 + 7^1 - 9^2 + 8^5}{-6^0 - 7^0 - 9^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6799 := \frac{-6^7 + 7^2 + 9^1 + 9^6}{6^1 - 7^2 - 9^0 + 9^2}$$

$$6803 := \frac{6^8 - 8^0 + 0^1 - 3^9}{6^3 + 8^0 + 0^1 + 3^3}$$

$$6805 := \frac{6^5 - 8^4 + 0^1 + 5^5}{-6^0 + 8^0 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$6809 := \frac{6^{11} + 8^0 + 0^1 + 9^2}{6^6 + 8^2 + 0^0 + 9^4}$$

$$6809 := \frac{6^{11} + 8^0 + 0^1 + 9^2}{6^6 + 8^2 + 0^0 + 9^4}$$

$$6813 := \frac{6^4 + 8^6 - 1^0 - 3^{10}}{6^0 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 3^3}$$

$$6817 := \frac{-6^6 - 8^5 + 1^0 + 7^8}{6^4 - 8^3 + 1^0 + 7^2}$$

$$6820 := \frac{-6^0 + 8^{12} - 2^{16} + 0^0}{6^9 - 8^3 - 2^{10} + 0^1}$$

$$6822 := \frac{-6^1 - 8^1 + 2^{12} + 2^{14}}{-6^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6823 := \frac{6^6 + 8^3 + 2^9 + 3^4}{6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$6823 := \frac{6^6 + 8^3 + 2^9 + 3^4}{6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 3^1}$$

$$6824 := \frac{6^4 + 8^4 + 2^{17} + 4^2}{6^1 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6824 := \frac{6^4 + 8^4 + 2^{17} + 4^2}{6^1 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6825 := \frac{6^4 + 8^6 + 2^{14} + 5^0}{6^1 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 5^2}$$

$$6825 := \frac{6^4 + 8^6 + 2^{14} + 5^0}{6^1 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 5^2}$$

$$6826 := \frac{-6^1 - 8^2 + 2^{13} - 6^4}{-6^0 - 8^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$6827 := \frac{6^4 + 8^2 + 2^{15} + 7^1}{6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$6827 := \frac{6^4 + 8^2 + 2^{15} + 7^1}{6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$6828 := \frac{6^2 + 8^4 + 2^4 + 8^6}{6^2 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$6828 := \frac{6^2 + 8^4 + 2^4 + 8^6}{6^2 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$6829 := \frac{6^1 + 8^4 + 2^{14} + 9^0}{-6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$6830 := \frac{6^5 - 8^3 + 3^{11} - 0^0}{-6^0 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 0^1}$$

$$6831 := \frac{6^2 + 8^4 + 3^{13} - 1^0}{6^3 + 8^1 + 3^2 + 1^0}$$

$$6832 := \frac{6^4 - 8^0 + 3^8 - 2^{10}}{-6^0 - 8^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6833 := \frac{-6^7 - 8^5 - 3^4 + 3^{12}}{6^0 + 8^0 + 3^1 + 3^3}$$

$$6834 := \frac{6^7 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 4^4}{6^2 + 8^0 + 3^1 + 4^0}$$

$$6834 := \frac{6^7 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 4^4}{6^2 + 8^0 + 3^1 + 4^0}$$

$$6835 := \frac{6^6 - 8^5 - 3^5 + 5^2}{-6^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$6836 := \frac{6^6 + 8^0 + 3^{13} + 6^7}{6^0 + 8^0 + 3^5 + 6^2}$$

$$6836 := \frac{6^6 + 8^0 + 3^{13} + 6^7}{6^0 + 8^0 + 3^5 + 6^2}$$

$$6837 := \frac{6^7 + 8^7 + 3^7 + 7^0}{6^0 + 8^0 + 3^1 + 7^3}$$

$$6837 := \frac{6^7 + 8^7 + 3^7 + 7^0}{6^0 + 8^0 + 3^1 + 7^3}$$

$$6838 := \frac{6^8 - 8^0 - 3^{13} + 8^8}{6^3 - 8^0 + 3^7 + 8^2}$$

$$6839 := \frac{6^2 - 8^0 + 3^5 + 9^4}{-6^0 - 8^1 + 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$6841 := \frac{-6^8 - 8^1 + 4^{18} + 1^0}{6^9 - 8^5 + 4^3 + 1^0}$$

$$6842 := \frac{-6^4 - 8^1 - 4^6 + 2^{15}}{6^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$6843 := \frac{6^6 + 8^3 + 4^1 + 3^6}{6^0 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 3^0}$$

$$6843 := \frac{6^6 + 8^3 + 4^1 + 3^6}{6^0 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 3^0}$$

$$6844 := \frac{6^2 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 4^{11}}{6^2 + 8^3 + 4^0 + 4^3}$$

$$6844 := \frac{6^2 + 8^1 + 4^5 + 4^{11}}{6^2 + 8^3 + 4^0 + 4^3}$$

$$6845 := \frac{6^2 - 8^3 + 4^2 + 5^8}{-6^0 - 8^0 + 4^3 - 5^1}$$

$$6846 := \frac{6^2 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 6^6}{6^0 + 8^1 + 4^1 + 6^0}$$

$$6846 := \frac{6^2 + 8^5 + 4^7 + 6^6}{6^0 + 8^1 + 4^1 + 6^0}$$

$$6847 := \frac{6^3 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 7^6}{6^1 + 8^1 + 4^0 + 7^1}$$

$$6847 := \frac{6^3 + 8^5 + 4^0 + 7^6}{6^1 + 8^1 + 4^0 + 7^1}$$

$$6848 := \frac{6^6 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 8^3}{6^0 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 8^0}$$

$$6848 := \frac{6^6 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 8^3}{6^0 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 8^0}$$

$$6849 := \frac{6^2 + 8^4 + 4^{11} + 9^0}{6^2 + 8^3 + 4^3 + 9^0}$$

$$6850 := \frac{6^6 + 8^5 + 5^7 + 0^0}{-6^0 - 8^0 + 5^2 + 0^1}$$

$$6852 := \frac{6^0 + 8^4 + 5^7 + 2^1}{6^0 + 8^1 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6852 := \frac{6^0 + 8^4 + 5^7 + 2^1}{6^0 + 8^1 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6853 := \frac{6^1 + 8^4 + 5^7 + 3^2}{6^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$6853 := \frac{6^1 + 8^4 + 5^7 + 3^2}{6^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$6854 := \frac{6^0 + 8^1 + 5^9 + 4^4}{6^3 + 8^2 + 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6854 := \frac{6^0 + 8^1 + 5^9 + 4^4}{6^3 + 8^2 + 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6855 := \frac{-6^5 - 8^6 + 5^5 + 5^9}{-6^3 + 8^3 - 5^2 - 5^2}$$

$$6857 := \frac{6^3 + 8^0 + 5^8 + 7^1}{6^1 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 7^2}$$

$$6857 := \frac{6^3 + 8^0 + 5^8 + 7^1}{6^1 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 7^2}$$

$$6858 := \frac{6^3 + 8^0 + 5^8 + 8^2}{6^2 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$6858 := \frac{6^3 + 8^0 + 5^8 + 8^2}{6^2 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$6859 := \frac{6^1 + 8^4 + 5^7 + 9^2}{6^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 9^1}$$

$$6859 := \frac{6^1 + 8^4 + 5^7 + 9^2}{6^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 9^1}$$

$$6862 := \frac{-6^2 - 8^5 + 6^6 - 2^7}{-6^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$6863 := \frac{6^1 + 8^3 - 6^3 + 3^8}{-6^0 - 8^0 + 6^1 - 3^1}$$

$$6864 := \frac{6^5 + 8^3 + 6^7 + 4^3}{6^0 + 8^0 + 6^2 + 4^1}$$

$$6864 := \frac{6^5 + 8^3 + 6^7 + 4^3}{6^0 + 8^0 + 6^2 + 4^1}$$

$$6864 := \frac{-6^6 + 8^6 - 6^6 - 4^6}{6^1 + 8^1 + 6^1 + 4^1}$$

$$6865 := \frac{-6^6 - 8^6 + 6^9 - 5^0}{6^0 + 8^0 + 6^4 + 5^3}$$

$$6866 := \frac{-6^1 + 8^7 + 6^4 - 6^8}{-6^0 + 8^2 - 6^0 - 6^0}$$

$$6867 := \frac{6^3 + 8^6 + 6^6 - 7^0}{6^0 + 8^0 + 6^2 + 7^1}$$

$$6868 := \frac{-6^3 + 8^2 + 6^6 - 8^5}{-6^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$6869 := \frac{6^6 - 8^4 + 6^6 + 9^2}{-6^0 - 8^0 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$6870 := \frac{6^{11} + 8^0 - 7^9 + 0^1}{6^6 - 8^2 + 7^3 + 0^1}$$

$$6871 := \frac{-6^5 + 8^2 + 7^6 - 1^0}{6^1 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 1^0}$$

$$6872 := \frac{6^0 - 8^3 + 7^1 + 2^{17}}{6^0 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 2^4}$$

$$6873 := \frac{6^6 + 8^3 + 7^1 - 3^9}{6^0 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$6874 := \frac{6^8 + 8^0 + 7^7 - 4^5}{6^1 - 8^0 + 7^3 + 4^2}$$

$$6875 := \frac{6^6 + 8^5 - 7^2 + 5^5}{-6^0 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 5^1}$$

$$6876 := \frac{6^0 - 8^5 + 7^7 - 6^2}{6^0 + 8^2 + 7^2 + 6^0}$$

$$6877 := \frac{6^7 + 8^4 + 7^4 + 7^4}{-6^0 + 8^0 - 7^1 + 7^2}$$

$$6878 := \frac{6^5 + 8^0 + 7^6 + 8^5}{6^1 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6878 := \frac{6^5 + 8^0 + 7^6 + 8^5}{6^1 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6879 := \frac{6^6 - 8^5 - 7^2 - 9^2}{-6^0 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$6880 := \frac{6^7 + 8^3 - 8^5 + 0^1}{6^2 - 8^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$6882 := \frac{6^3 + 8^5 + 8^7 - 2^{16}}{6^2 + 8^1 + 8^3 - 2^8}$$

$$6883 := \frac{-6^3 + 8^7 + 8^8 + 3^9}{6^3 + 8^2 - 8^4 + 3^8}$$

$$6884 := \frac{-6^2 - 8^3 + 8^6 - 4^1}{6^1 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 4^2}$$

$$6885 := \frac{-6^0 - 8^3 + 8^6 - 5^0}{6^1 - 8^0 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$6887 := \frac{6^1 - 8^2 - 8^3 + 7^6}{6^0 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$6888 := \frac{6^5 + 8^1 - 8^4 + 8^7}{-6^3 + 8^0 + 8^1 + 8^3}$$

$$6889 := \frac{6^2 - 8^3 - 8^3 + 9^6}{-6^1 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 9^2}$$

$$6890 := \frac{6^1 + 8^6 + 9^4 - 0^0}{6^2 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 0^0}$$

$$6892 := \frac{-6^0 + 8^6 + 9^1 - 2^8}{-6^0 + 8^1 - 9^0 + 2^5}$$

$$6893 := \frac{-6^4 + 8^4 - 9^3 + 3^{11}}{6^1 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 3^1}$$

$$6894 := \frac{6^4 - 8^5 + 9^5 - 4^0}{6^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$6895 := \frac{-6^3 + 8^6 + 9^2 + 5^0}{6^1 + 8^1 - 9^0 + 5^2}$$

$$6896 := \frac{-6^0 - 8^4 + 9^5 + 6^3}{-6^0 - 8^0 + 9^1 + 6^0}$$

$$6897 := \frac{6^3 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 7^7}{6^1 + 8^2 + 9^1 + 7^2}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 6897 := \frac{6^3 + 8^1 + 9^5 + 7^7}{6^1 + 8^2 + 9^1 + 7^2} & 6925 := \frac{6^0 + 9^2 + 2^{15} + 5^6}{6^0 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 5^0} & 6943 := \frac{6^6 + 9^6 + 4^{12} + 3^7}{6^3 + 9^2 + 4^2 + 3^7} \\
 6898 := \frac{6^3 + 8^0 + 9^6 - 8^3}{-6^1 + 8^0 + 9^2 + 8^0} & 6926 := \frac{6^0 + 9^4 - 2^{14} + 6^7}{6^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 6^2} & 6943 := \frac{6^6 + 9^6 + 4^{12} + 3^7}{6^3 + 9^2 + 4^2 + 3^7} \\
 6899 := \frac{6^6 - 8^5 - 9^1 - 9^2}{-6^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 9^0} & 6927 := \frac{-6^4 + 9^5 + 2^6 - 7^4}{-6^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 7^1} & 6944 := \frac{6^7 + 9^8 - 4^0 - 4^8}{-6^0 - 9^5 - 4^4 + 4^8} \\
 6902 := \frac{6^1 + 9^6 - 0^0 + 2^3}{6^2 + 9^1 + 0^1 + 2^5} & 6928 := \frac{6^7 - 9^4 - 2^{16} + 8^0}{-6^0 - 9^0 - 2^5 + 8^2} & 6945 := \frac{6^5 + 9^6 + 4^7 - 5^0}{6^1 + 9^1 + 4^3 + 5^0} \\
 6903 := \frac{6^7 + 9^1 + 0^1 - 3^{10}}{6^1 - 9^0 + 0^1 + 3^3} & 6929 := \frac{6^5 + 9^4 - 2^{12} + 9^5}{6^1 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 9^0} & 6947 := \frac{-6^5 + 9^3 + 4^8 - 7^5}{-6^0 - 9^0 + 4^0 + 7^1} \\
 6904 := \frac{6^3 - 9^1 + 0^0 + 4^9}{6^2 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 4^0} & 6930 := \frac{6^9 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 0^1}{6^4 + 9^2 + 3^4 + 0^1} & 6948 := \frac{6^6 + 9^1 - 4^0 - 8^5}{-6^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 8^0} \\
 6908 := \frac{-6^4 + 9^6 - 0^0 - 8^5}{6^1 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 8^2} & 6930 := \frac{6^9 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 0^1}{6^4 + 9^2 + 3^4 + 0^1} & 6949 := \frac{-6^3 + 9^4 + 4^6 + 9^5}{-6^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 9^1} \\
 6912 := \frac{6^5 + 9^4 - 1^0 - 2^9}{-6^0 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 2^0} & 6932 := \frac{6^4 + 9^6 + 3^1 + 2^{10}}{6^0 + 9^1 + 3^1 + 2^6} & 6950 := \frac{6^8 - 9^6 - 5^8 + 0^1}{-6^1 - 9^1 + 5^3 - 0^0} \\
 6913 := \frac{6^8 - 9^0 + 1^0 + 3^5}{6^3 - 9^0 + 1^0 + 3^3} & 6933 := \frac{6^4 + 9^4 + 3^7 + 3^{11}}{6^1 + 9^1 + 3^1 + 3^2} & 6952 := \frac{6^1 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 2^{19}}{6^0 + 9^2 + 5^0 + 2^0} \\
 6915 := \frac{6^8 + 9^3 - 1^0 + 5^0}{6^2 + 9^2 + 1^0 + 5^3} & 6933 := \frac{6^4 + 9^4 + 3^7 + 3^{11}}{6^1 + 9^1 + 3^1 + 3^2} & 6952 := \frac{6^1 + 9^5 + 5^4 + 2^{19}}{6^0 + 9^2 + 5^0 + 2^0} \\
 6920 := \frac{6^5 - 9^3 - 2^7 + 0^0}{-6^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 0^1} & 6934 := \frac{6^1 + 9^0 + 3^{11} + 4^8}{6^0 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 4^2} & 6953 := \frac{6^8 - 9^6 + 5^8 - 3^7}{6^1 + 9^1 + 5^3 + 3^4} \\
 6921 := \frac{-6^5 + 9^5 + 2^{12} - 1^0}{-6^0 + 9^1 - 2^0 + 1^0} & 6935 := \frac{6^1 + 9^4 + 3^5 + 5^3}{-6^1 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 5^1} & 6954 := \frac{-6^1 + 9^4 - 5^4 + 4^5}{-6^0 - 9^0 - 5^0 + 4^1} \\
 6922 := \frac{6^4 + 9^6 + 2^0 + 2^8}{6^2 + 9^0 + 2^3 + 2^5} & 6936 := \frac{-6^2 + 9^3 + 3^{11} + 6^7}{-6^1 + 9^1 + 3^3 + 6^2} & 6955 := \frac{-6^4 + 9^4 - 5^2 + 5^6}{6^1 - 9^0 - 5^0 - 5^0} \\
 6922 := \frac{6^4 + 9^6 + 2^0 + 2^8}{6^2 + 9^0 + 2^3 + 2^5} & 6937 := \frac{6^2 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 7^6}{6^1 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 7^1} & 6956 := \frac{-6^3 - 9^3 + 5^3 + 6^5}{-6^0 + 9^0 - 5^1 + 6^1} \\
 6923 := \frac{6^5 + 9^3 + 2^{13} + 3^{11}}{6^1 + 9^1 + 2^2 + 3^2} & 6938 := \frac{-6^3 + 9^2 + 3^8 + 8^3}{6^0 + 9^0 - 3^2 + 8^1} & 6957 := \frac{6^8 + 9^7 + 5^3 + 7^3}{6^3 + 9^2 + 5^4 + 7^1} \\
 6923 := \frac{6^5 + 9^3 + 2^{13} + 3^{11}}{6^1 + 9^1 + 2^2 + 3^2} & 6939 := \frac{6^5 + 9^6 + 3^3 + 9^7}{6^2 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 9^3} & 6957 := \frac{6^8 + 9^7 + 5^3 + 7^3}{6^3 + 9^2 + 5^4 + 7^1} \\
 6924 := \frac{6^7 + 9^3 - 2^0 + 4^8}{6^0 + 9^0 + 2^5 + 4^2} & 6939 := \frac{6^8 + 9^8 + 3^8 - 9^8}{6^3 + 9^3 + 3^3 - 9^3} & 6958 := \frac{6^5 - 9^3 - 5^2 - 8^2}{-6^0 - 9^0 - 5^1 + 8^1} \\
 6925 := \frac{6^0 + 9^2 + 2^{15} + 5^6}{6^0 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 5^0} & 6942 := \frac{6^5 - 9^1 + 4^0 + 2^{17}}{6^0 + 9^0 + 4^2 + 2^1} & 6959 := \frac{6^7 - 9^0 - 5^7 + 9^0}{6^1 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 9^1}
 \end{array}$$

$$6959 := \frac{6^7 + 9^7 - 5^7 - 9^7}{6^1 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 9^1}$$

$$6962 := \frac{6^0 - 9^4 + 6^9 + 2^{16}}{-6^0 + 9^3 + 6^3 + 2^9}$$

$$6963 := \frac{6^2 + 9^6 + 6^6 + 3^{13}}{6^1 + 9^1 + 6^3 + 3^4}$$

$$6963 := \frac{6^2 + 9^6 + 6^6 + 3^{13}}{6^1 + 9^1 + 6^3 + 3^4}$$

$$6964 := \frac{-6^4 - 9^2 + 6^7 + 4^0}{-6^0 + 9^0 + 6^2 + 4^1}$$

$$6965 := \frac{-6^0 + 9^6 + 6^6 - 5^0}{6^0 - 9^1 + 6^3 - 5^3}$$

$$6966 := \frac{-6^0 + 9^0 - 6^4 + 6^7}{-6^0 - 9^0 + 6^1 + 6^2}$$

$$6967 := \frac{-6^4 - 9^1 + 6^7 + 7^2}{-6^0 - 9^1 + 6^0 + 7^2}$$

$$6968 := \frac{-6^4 + 9^2 + 6^7 - 8^0}{6^1 - 9^0 + 6^2 - 8^0}$$

$$6969 := \frac{-6^5 - 9^1 + 6^8 + 9^3}{6^1 + 9^1 + 6^3 + 9^1}$$

$$6972 := \frac{6^4 + 9^5 + 7^4 + 2^1}{6^1 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$6972 := \frac{6^5 + 9^5 + 7^5 + 2^5}{-6^1 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 2^1}$$

$$6973 := \frac{6^7 + 9^7 + 7^7 + 3^9}{6^2 + 9^2 + 7^0 + 3^6}$$

$$6973 := \frac{6^7 + 9^7 + 7^7 + 3^9}{6^2 + 9^2 + 7^0 + 3^6}$$

$$6974 := \frac{6^1 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 4^3}{-6^0 - 9^0 - 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6975 := \frac{6^7 - 9^1 + 7^6 - 5^0}{6^1 + 9^0 + 7^2 + 5^0}$$

$$6976 := \frac{6^2 + 9^4 + 7^3 + 6^2}{6^0 + 9^0 - 7^1 + 6^1}$$

$$6977 := \frac{-6^2 + 9^4 - 7^4 + 7^5}{6^1 - 9^0 - 7^0 - 7^0}$$

$$6978 := \frac{6^7 - 9^5 + 7^4 + 8^1}{-6^0 + 9^2 - 7^2 + 8^0}$$

$$6979 := \frac{-6^1 + 9^2 + 7^3 + 9^4}{-6^1 - 9^0 - 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$6982 := \frac{6^5 - 9^3 - 8^0 - 2^6}{-6^0 - 9^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6983 := \frac{6^6 + 9^2 - 8^5 - 3^1}{-6^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$6984 := \frac{6^5 - 9^3 + 8^0 - 4^3}{-6^0 - 9^0 - 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$6985 := \frac{6^6 + 9^2 - 8^5 + 5^0}{-6^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 5^0}$$

$$6986 := \frac{-6^0 + 9^6 - 8^1 - 6^7}{6^0 - 9^1 + 8^1 + 6^2}$$

$$6987 := \frac{6^3 + 9^5 + 8^6 - 7^1}{6^2 + 9^0 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$6988 := \frac{-6^7 + 9^6 - 8^0 + 8^2}{6^2 - 9^1 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$6989 := \frac{6^6 + 9^1 - 8^5 + 9^2}{-6^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$6992 := \frac{6^5 + 9^1 - 9^3 - 2^6}{-6^0 - 9^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$6993 := \frac{6^8 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 3^8}{6^3 + 9^1 + 9^1 + 3^2}$$

$$6993 := \frac{6^8 + 9^4 + 9^4 + 3^8}{6^3 + 9^1 + 9^1 + 3^2}$$

$$6994 := \frac{6^1 + 9^6 + 9^7 + 4^5}{6^1 + 9^1 + 9^3 + 4^2}$$

$$6994 := \frac{6^1 + 9^6 + 9^7 + 4^5}{6^1 + 9^1 + 9^3 + 4^2}$$

$$6996 := \frac{-6^2 - 9^3 + 9^5 + 6^6}{-6^0 + 9^0 + 9^1 + 6^1}$$

$$6997 := \frac{6^5 - 9^0 - 9^3 - 7^2}{-6^1 - 9^0 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$6998 := \frac{6^1 - 9^2 + 9^4 + 8^3}{6^0 + 9^0 - 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$6999 := \frac{6^6 + 9^1 - 9^3 + 9^5}{6^1 - 9^0 + 9^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7022 := \frac{7^0 + 0^0 + 2^{14} + 2^{15}}{7^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 2^2}$$

$$7022 := \frac{7^0 + 0^0 + 2^{14} + 2^{15}}{7^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 2^2}$$

$$7023 := \frac{-7^2 - 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8}{-7^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$7024 := \frac{-7^4 + 0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7}{-7^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$7025 := \frac{7^4 + 0^0 + 2^{17} + 5^0}{7^0 + 0^0 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$7025 := \frac{7^4 + 0^0 + 2^{17} + 5^0}{7^0 + 0^0 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$7026 := \frac{7^3 + 0^0 + 2^{18} + 6^6}{7^1 + 0^1 + 2^0 + 6^2}$$

$$7026 := \frac{7^3 + 0^0 + 2^{18} + 6^6}{7^1 + 0^1 + 2^0 + 6^2}$$

$$7032 := \frac{7^3 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 2^7}{-7^0 - 0^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$7034 := \frac{7^6 + 0^1 - 3^9 + 4^{10}}{7^3 - 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^3}$$

$$7035 := \frac{7^7 + 0^0 + 3^8 + 5^2}{7^0 + 0^0 - 3^2 + 5^3}$$

$$7036 := \frac{7^2 + 0^1 + 3^{11} - 6^4}{-7^0 - 0^0 - 3^2 + 6^2}$$

$$7037 := \frac{7^3 + 0^1 + 3^{13} + 7^5}{-7^1 + 0^1 + 3^5 - 7^1}$$

$$7038 := \frac{7^6 + 0^1 + 3^{13} - 8^6}{7^4 + 0^1 - 3^7 - 8^1}$$

$$7039 := \frac{-7^5 + 0^0 - 3^2 + 9^5}{7^0 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 9^0}$$

$$7042 := \frac{7^6 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 2^{11}}{7^1 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 2^3}$$

$$7042 := \frac{7^6 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 2^{11}}{7^1 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 2^3}$$

$$7043 := \frac{-7^5 + 0^1 + 4^2 + 3^{10}}{7^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 3^1}$$

$$7048 := \frac{7^6 - 0^0 + 4^8 + 8^2}{7^0 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 8^1}$$

$$7049 := \frac{-7^4 + 0^1 - 4^4 + 9^5}{-7^0 - 0^0 + 4^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7052 := \frac{7^3 + 0^1 + 5^9 - 2^6}{7^3 - 0^0 - 5^0 - 2^6}$$

$$7053 := \frac{-7^2 - 0^0 + 5^7 + 3^8}{7^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$7054 := \frac{-7^4 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 4^7}{-7^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$7056 := \frac{-7^6 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 6^7}{-7^0 + 0^1 + 5^2 - 6^0}$$

$$7058 := \frac{7^6 + 0^1 - 5^4 - 8^4}{7^1 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 8^1}$$

$$7062 := \frac{7^0 + 0^0 + 6^7 - 2^{15}}{7^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 2^5}$$

$$7063 := \frac{7^7 + 0^0 - 6^7 + 3^5}{7^2 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 3^3}$$

$$7064 := \frac{-7^3 - 0^0 + 6^7 - 4^6}{7^0 + 0^0 + 6^2 + 4^0}$$

$$7065 := \frac{7^{11} + 0^0 + 6^6 - 5^1}{-7^2 + 0^0 + 6^7 - 5^1}$$

$$7067 := \frac{7^3 + 0^1 + 6^7 + 7^4}{-7^1 - 0^0 - 6^0 + 7^2}$$

$$7068 := \frac{7^7 + 0^0 - 6^7 + 8^6}{7^2 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 8^2}$$

$$7072 := \frac{-7^0 + 0^1 + 7^8 - 2^{13}}{7^3 + 0^1 + 7^3 + 2^7}$$

$$7082 := \frac{-7^3 - 0^0 - 8^4 + 2^{15}}{7^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$7083 := \frac{-7^0 + 0^1 + 8^6 - 3^{11}}{7^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 3^2}$$

$$7085 := \frac{-7^0 + 0^0 + 8^6 + 5^0}{-7^0 - 0^0 + 8^2 - 5^2}$$

$$7086 := \frac{7^0 + 0^0 + 8^6 + 6^2}{-7^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 6^2}$$

$$7089 := \frac{-7^4 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 9^5}{-7^0 - 0^0 + 8^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7092 := \frac{7^6 + 0^1 - 9^2 - 2^{12}}{7^1 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 2^3}$$

$$7093 := \frac{7^0 + 0^0 - 9^4 + 3^{12}}{7^0 + 0^0 - 9^1 + 3^4}$$

$$7094 := \frac{7^3 + 0^1 - 9^1 + 4^9}{7^2 + 0^0 - 9^1 - 4^1}$$

$$7095 := \frac{7^0 + 0^1 - 9^2 + 5^7}{7^0 + 0^1 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$7096 := \frac{7^2 + 0^1 - 9^3 + 6^5}{-7^0 - 0^0 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$7123 := \frac{7^2 + 1^0 + 2^9 + 3^8}{-7^0 - 1^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$7124 := \frac{7^7 + 1^0 + 2^{16} + 4^8}{7^0 + 1^0 + 2^7 + 4^1}$$

$$7124 := \frac{7^7 + 1^0 + 2^{16} + 4^8}{7^0 + 1^0 + 2^7 + 4^1}$$

$$7125 := \frac{-7^1 + 1^0 + 2^8 + 5^7}{7^0 + 1^0 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$7126 := \frac{7^7 + 1^0 - 2^{19} + 6^2}{7^0 + 1^0 + 2^2 + 6^2}$$

$$7127 := \frac{-7^5 + 1^0 - 2^{13} + 7^6}{7^0 + 1^0 + 2^2 + 7^1}$$

$$7128 := \frac{7^2 - 1^0 + 2^{11} + 8^8}{7^4 + 1^0 + 2^4 - 8^2}$$

$$7133 := \frac{7^7 - 1^0 + 3^3 + 3^{14}}{7^2 - 1^0 + 3^2 + 3^6}$$

$$7137 := \frac{-7^4 - 1^0 + 3^{11} - 7^6}{-7^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 7^1}$$

$$7143 := \frac{7^7 - 1^0 - 4^7 + 3^0}{7^2 - 1^0 - 4^2 + 3^4}$$

$$7146 := \frac{7^5 + 1^0 + 4^{10} - 6^5}{7^2 - 1^0 + 4^3 + 6^2}$$

$$7159 := \frac{-7^4 - 1^0 + 5^4 + 9^5}{7^0 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 9^0}$$

$$7162 := \frac{7^4 - 1^0 + 6^6 + 2^{16}}{7^1 + 1^1 + 6^1 + 2^1}$$

$$7164 := \frac{7^7 + 1^0 + 6^8 + 4^9}{7^5 - 1^0 - 6^2 - 4^7}$$

$$7169 := \frac{-7^3 - 1^0 + 6^7 - 9^0}{7^0 + 1^0 + 6^2 + 9^0}$$

$$7182 := \frac{-7^0 - 1^0 + 8^6 + 2^{18}}{7^1 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 2^6}$$

$$7203 := \frac{7^2 - 2^{19} + 0^0 + 3^{12}}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 3^0}$$

$$7204 := \frac{7^7 + 2^9 + 0^0 - 4^9}{-7^0 + 2^4 - 0^0 + 4^3}$$

$$7205 := \frac{7^7 - 2^{11} + 0^1 - 5^3}{7^2 + 2^6 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$7206 := \frac{-7^5 - 2^{10} - 0^0 + 6^6}{7^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 6^0}$$

$$7207 := \frac{-7^4 + 2^3 + 0^1 + 7^5}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 7^0}$$

$$7208 := \frac{-7^4 - 2^8 + 0^0 + 8^6}{7^2 - 2^2 - 0^0 - 8^1}$$

$$7209 := \frac{-7^4 + 2^{10} + 0^1 + 9^5}{-7^0 - 2^0 + 0^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7212 := \frac{-7^6 - 2^8 + 1^0 + 2^{18}}{7^0 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 2^4}$$

$$7213 := \frac{-7^0 + 2^{14} - 1^0 + 3^9}{7^0 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$7214 := \frac{-7^6 - 2^{18} - 1^0 + 4^{12}}{7^4 - 2^7 - 1^0 + 4^0}$$

$$7215 := \frac{7^4 + 2^{19} + 1^0 + 5^1}{7^1 + 2^6 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7215 := \frac{7^4 + 2^{19} + 1^0 + 5^1}{7^1 + 2^6 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7216 := \frac{-7^2 - 2^9 + 1^0 + 6^5}{7^0 - 2^1 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$7219 := \frac{7^2 + 2^7 - 1^0 + 9^8}{-7^3 - 2^8 + 1^0 + 9^4}$$

$$7220 := \frac{-7^4 - 2^{11} + 2^{19} + 0^0}{7^1 + 2^0 + 2^6 + 0^1}$$

$$7221 := \frac{7^5 + 2^{13} + 2^{15} + 1^0}{7^0 + 2^1 + 2^2 + 1^0}$$

$$7221 := \frac{7^5 + 2^{13} + 2^{15} + 1^0}{7^0 + 2^1 + 2^2 + 1^0}$$

$$7222 := \frac{-7^5 - 2^0 - 2^{14} + 2^{19}}{7^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 2^6}$$

$$7223 := \frac{7^3 + 2^{13} + 2^{18} + 3^{11}}{7^0 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 3^3}$$

$$7223 := \frac{7^3 + 2^{13} + 2^{18} + 3^{11}}{7^0 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 3^3}$$

$$7224 := \frac{-7^6 + 2^0 + 2^{17} + 4^5}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$7225 := \frac{7^4 + 2^{15} + 2^{20} + 5^1}{7^0 + 2^3 + 2^4 + 5^3}$$

$$7225 := \frac{7^4 + 2^{15} + 2^{20} + 5^1}{7^0 + 2^3 + 2^4 + 5^3}$$

$$7226 := \frac{7^7 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 6^3}{7^2 + 2^5 + 2^5 + 6^0}$$

$$7226 := \frac{7^7 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 6^3}{7^2 + 2^5 + 2^5 + 6^0}$$

$$7227 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{13} + 2^{15} + 7^4}{7^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$7227 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{13} + 2^{15} + 7^4}{7^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$7228 := \frac{-7^6 + 2^0 + 2^6 + 8^6}{7^0 + 2^1 + 2^4 + 8^0}$$

$$7229 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{19} + 9^4}{7^0 + 2^3 + 2^6 + 9^0}$$

$$7229 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{19} + 9^4}{7^0 + 2^3 + 2^6 + 9^0}$$

$$7230 := \frac{7^7 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 0^1}{-7^0 + 2^5 + 3^4 + 0^0}$$

$$7231 := \frac{-7^0 + 2^{20} - 3^4 + 1^0}{7^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 1^0}$$

$$7232 := \frac{7^7 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 2^{17}}{7^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 2^7}$$

$$7232 := \frac{7^7 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 2^{17}}{7^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 2^7}$$

$$7233 := \frac{7^6 + 2^{18} + 3^0 + 3^{11}}{7^0 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 3^2}$$

$$7233 := \frac{7^6 + 2^{18} + 3^0 + 3^{11}}{7^0 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 3^2}$$

$$7234 := \frac{7^5 + 2^9 + 3^{12} + 4^5}{7^0 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3}$$

$$7235 := \frac{7^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^3}{7^0 + 2^2 + 3^2 + 5^1}$$

$$7235 := \frac{7^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^3}{7^0 + 2^2 + 3^2 + 5^1}$$

$$7236 := \frac{7^6 + 2^{15} + 3^5 + 6^4}{7^0 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 6^0}$$

$$7236 := \frac{7^6 + 2^{15} + 3^5 + 6^4}{7^0 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 6^0}$$

$$7237 := \frac{7^6 + 2^6 + 3^{11} + 7^6}{7^0 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 7^2}$$

$$7237 := \frac{7^6 + 2^6 + 3^{11} + 7^6}{7^0 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 7^2}$$

$$7238 := \frac{7^7 + 2^2 + 3^2 + 8^6}{7^0 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 8^2}$$

$$7238 := \frac{7^7 + 2^2 + 3^2 + 8^6}{7^0 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 8^2}$$

$$7239 := \frac{7^6 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 9^2}{7^0 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7239 := \frac{7^6 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 9^2}{7^0 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7240 := \frac{-7^3 - 2^5 + 4^8 - 0^0}{7^0 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 0^1}$$

$$7241 := \frac{7^6 - 2^{11} + 4^4 - 1^0}{7^1 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 1^0}$$

$$7242 := \frac{-7^3 + 2^0 - 4^2 + 2^{16}}{7^0 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 2^1}$$

$$7243 := \frac{7^4 + 2^{19} + 4^6 + 3^9}{7^0 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 3^2}$$

$$7243 := \frac{7^4 + 2^{19} + 4^6 + 3^9}{7^0 + 2^1 + 4^3 + 3^2}$$

$$7244 := \frac{-7^3 - 2^0 + 4^1 + 4^8}{-7^0 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 4^1}$$

$$7245 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{15} + 4^8 + 5^5}{7^0 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^1}$$

$$7245 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{15} + 4^8 + 5^5}{7^0 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^1}$$

$$7246 := \frac{7^4 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 6^7}{7^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 6^2}$$

$$7246 := \frac{7^4 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 6^7}{7^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 6^2}$$

$$7247 := \frac{-7^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$7248 := \frac{-7^4 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 8^3}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$7249 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{13} - 4^4 + 9^4}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 9^0}$$

$$7250 := \frac{7^6 - 2^{10} - 5^4 + 0^1}{7^1 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 0^1}$$

$$7251 := \frac{7^6 + 2^1 + 5^7 + 1^0}{-7^0 + 2^1 + 5^2 + 1^0}$$

$$7252 := \frac{7^3 + 2^7 + 5^8 + 2^9}{7^0 + 2^4 + 5^1 + 2^5}$$

$$7252 := \frac{7^3 + 2^7 + 5^8 + 2^9}{7^0 + 2^4 + 5^1 + 2^5}$$

$$7253 := \frac{7^2 + 2^{17} + 5^3 + 3^8}{7^0 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 3^2}$$

$$7253 := \frac{7^2 + 2^{17} + 5^3 + 3^8}{7^0 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 3^2}$$

$$7254 := \frac{7^8 + 2^9 + 5^3 + 4^{11}}{7^3 + 2^0 + 5^1 + 4^5}$$

$$7254 := \frac{7^8 + 2^9 + 5^3 + 4^{11}}{7^3 + 2^0 + 5^1 + 4^5}$$

$$7255 := \frac{-7^3 + 2^{11} - 5^2 + 5^7}{7^0 + 2^2 + 5^0 + 5^1}$$

$$7256 := \frac{7^5 + 2^7 + 5^4 + 6^7}{7^1 + 2^3 + 5^2 + 6^0}$$

$$7256 := \frac{7^5 + 2^7 + 5^4 + 6^7}{7^1 + 2^3 + 5^2 + 6^0}$$

$$7257 := \frac{7^2 + 2^{15} + 5^5 + 7^3}{7^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$7257 := \frac{7^2 + 2^{15} + 5^5 + 7^3}{7^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$7258 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{18} + 5^7 + 8^6}{7^2 + 2^0 + 5^2 + 8^1}$$

$$7258 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{18} + 5^7 + 8^6}{7^2 + 2^0 + 5^2 + 8^1}$$

$$7259 := \frac{7^8 + 2^{16} + 5^8 + 9^0}{7^0 + 2^1 + 5^3 + 9^3}$$

$$7259 := \frac{7^8 + 2^{16} + 5^8 + 9^0}{7^0 + 2^1 + 5^3 + 9^3}$$

$$7260 := \frac{7^7 + 2^{12} + 6^0 + 0^1}{7^2 + 2^6 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$7260 := \frac{7^7 + 2^{12} + 6^0 + 0^1}{7^2 + 2^6 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$7262 := \frac{7^8 + 2^0 + 6^5 + 2^{18}}{7^3 + 2^4 + 6^3 + 2^8}$$

$$7262 := \frac{7^8 + 2^0 + 6^5 + 2^{18}}{7^3 + 2^4 + 6^3 + 2^8}$$

$$7263 := \frac{7^7 + 2^{19} + 6^6 + 3^2}{7^0 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 3^3}$$

$$7263 := \frac{7^7 + 2^{19} + 6^6 + 3^2}{7^0 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 3^3}$$

$$7264 := \frac{-7^0 - 2^9 + 6^5 + 4^0}{-7^0 - 2^0 - 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7265 := \frac{7^3 + 2^{16} + 6^4 + 5^7}{7^1 + 2^1 + 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$7265 := \frac{7^3 + 2^{16} + 6^4 + 5^7}{7^1 + 2^1 + 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$7266 := \frac{7^0 - 2^9 + 6^0 + 6^5}{7^0 - 2^1 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$7267 := \frac{7^3 + 2^{19} + 6^7 + 7^8}{7^3 + 2^1 + 6^3 + 7^3}$$

$$7267 := \frac{7^3 + 2^{19} + 6^7 + 7^8}{7^3 + 2^1 + 6^3 + 7^3}$$

$$7268 := \frac{-7^4 + 2^0 - 6^4 + 8^5}{7^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$7269 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{17} + 6^8 + 9^4}{7^0 + 2^5 + 6^3 + 9^0}$$

$$7269 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{17} + 6^8 + 9^4}{7^0 + 2^5 + 6^3 + 9^0}$$

$$7271 := \frac{-7^2 + 2^{16} - 7^2 + 1^0}{-7^0 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 1^0}$$

$$7272 := \frac{7^5 + 2^5 + 7^6 + 2^{15}}{7^1 + 2^0 + 7^1 + 2^3}$$

$$7272 := \frac{7^5 + 2^5 + 7^6 + 2^{15}}{7^1 + 2^0 + 7^1 + 2^3}$$

$$7273 := \frac{7^3 + 2^9 + 7^6 + 3^9}{7^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 3^1}$$

$$7273 := \frac{7^3 + 2^9 + 7^6 + 3^9}{7^1 + 2^1 + 7^1 + 3^1}$$

$$7274 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{13} + 7^5 + 4^6}{7^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$7274 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{13} + 7^5 + 4^6}{7^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$7275 := \frac{-7^2 + 2^{13} + 7^5 - 5^5}{-7^0 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7276 := \frac{-7^3 - 2^8 - 7^4 + 6^6}{-7^0 - 2^0 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$7277 := \frac{-7^0 + 2^{16} + 7^1 - 7^2}{-7^0 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 7^1}$$

$$7278 := \frac{7^1 + 2^{16} - 7^2 + 8^1}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 8^1}$$

$$7279 := \frac{7^3 + 2^5 + 7^3 + 9^4}{7^0 - 2^1 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$7280 := \frac{-7^1 + 2^{16} - 8^1 - 0^0}{7^1 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$7281 := \frac{-7^1 + 2^{16} - 8^0 + 1^0}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 8^1 + 1^0}$$

$$7282 := \frac{7^6 + 2^0 + 8^4 + 2^{11}}{7^0 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 2^2}$$

$$7282 := \frac{7^6 + 2^0 + 8^4 + 2^{11}}{7^0 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 2^2}$$

$$7283 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{16} + 8^0 + 3^2}{7^0 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 3^1}$$

$$7283 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{16} + 8^0 + 3^2}{7^0 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 3^1}$$

$$7284 := \frac{7^2 + 2^{17} - 8^1 - 4^0}{7^0 + 2^3 + 8^1 + 4^0}$$

$$7285 := \frac{7^2 + 2^{17} + 8^1 + 5^0}{7^0 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$7285 := \frac{7^2 + 2^{17} + 8^1 + 5^0}{7^0 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$7286 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{16} + 8^0 + 6^2}{7^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$7286 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{16} + 8^0 + 6^2}{7^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$7287 := \frac{-7^0 + 2^{16} - 8^0 + 7^2}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$7288 := \frac{-7^1 + 2^{16} - 8^0 + 8^2}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$7289 := \frac{7^5 + 2^{20} + 8^9 + 9^3}{7^5 + 2^9 + 8^3 + 9^3}$$

$$7289 := \frac{7^5 + 2^{20} + 8^9 + 9^3}{7^5 + 2^9 + 8^3 + 9^3}$$

$$7290 := \frac{-7^1 + 2^{16} + 9^2 + 0^1}{7^1 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 0^1}$$

$$7291 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{16} + 9^2 + 1^0}{7^0 - 2^1 + 9^1 + 1^0}$$

$$7292 := \frac{7^3 + 2^4 + 9^1 + 2^{18}}{7^0 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 2^5}$$

$$7292 := \frac{7^3 + 2^4 + 9^1 + 2^{18}}{7^0 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 2^5}$$

$$7293 := \frac{7^4 + 2^{11} + 9^3 + 3^{11}}{7^1 + 2^3 + 9^0 + 3^2}$$

$$7293 := \frac{7^4 + 2^{11} + 9^3 + 3^{11}}{7^1 + 2^3 + 9^0 + 3^2}$$

$$7294 := \frac{7^5 + 2^{13} + 9^2 + 4^6}{7^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$7294 := \frac{7^5 + 2^{13} + 9^2 + 4^6}{7^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$7295 := \frac{7^7 + 2^{12} + 9^0 + 5^8}{7^0 + 2^5 + 9^1 + 5^3}$$

$$7295 := \frac{7^7 + 2^{12} + 9^0 + 5^8}{7^0 + 2^5 + 9^1 + 5^3}$$

$$7296 := \frac{7^7 + 2^3 + 9^5 + 6^3}{7^1 + 2^5 + 9^2 + 6^0}$$

$$7297 := \frac{7^3 + 2^1 + 9^5 + 7^7}{7^0 + 2^5 + 9^2 + 7^1}$$

$$7297 := \frac{7^3 + 2^1 + 9^5 + 7^7}{7^0 + 2^5 + 9^2 + 7^1}$$

$$7298 := \frac{7^0 + 2^{16} + 9^2 + 8^2}{-7^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 8^1}$$

$$7299 := \frac{7^6 + 2^9 + 9^1 + 9^6}{7^1 + 2^6 + 9^1 + 9^1}$$

$$7302 := \frac{7^5 - 3^7 + 0^1 - 2^4}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 2^0}$$

$$7305 := \frac{-7^0 - 3^9 - 0^0 + 5^7}{7^0 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 5^1}$$

$$7307 := \frac{-7^1 - 3^7 + 0^0 + 7^5}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 7^0}$$

$$7308 := \frac{7^6 - 3^6 + 0^1 + 8^1}{7^1 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 8^1}$$

$$7309 := \frac{7^5 - 3^7 - 0^0 - 9^0}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 9^0}$$

$$7310 := \frac{7^5 - 3^7 - 1^0 + 0^0}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 0^0}$$

$$7311 := \frac{7^5 - 3^7 + 1^0 + 1^0}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 1^0}$$

$$7313 := \frac{-7^5 + 3^{10} + 1^0 + 3^{11}}{7^0 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 3^3}$$

$$7315 := \frac{-7^5 + 3^8 + 1^0 + 5^8}{7^2 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7317 := \frac{7^6 - 3^{12} + 1^0 + 7^7}{-7^0 + 3^2 - 1^0 + 7^2}$$

$$7320 := \frac{7^3 + 3^0 + 2^{16} + 0^1}{7^0 + 3^1 + 2^2 + 0^0}$$

$$7320 := \frac{7^3 + 3^0 + 2^{16} + 0^1}{7^0 + 3^1 + 2^2 + 0^0}$$

$$7321 := \frac{7^3 + 3^2 + 2^{16} + 1^0}{7^0 + 3^1 + 2^2 + 1^0}$$

$$7321 := \frac{7^3 + 3^2 + 2^{16} + 1^0}{7^0 + 3^1 + 2^2 + 1^0}$$

$$7322 := \frac{7^3 + 3^1 + 2^4 + 2^{16}}{7^0 + 3^1 + 2^0 + 2^2}$$

$$7322 := \frac{7^3 + 3^1 + 2^4 + 2^{16}}{7^0 + 3^1 + 2^0 + 2^2}$$

$$7323 := \frac{7^3 + 3^0 + 2^{16} + 3^3}{7^0 + 3^0 + 2^2 + 3^1}$$

$$7324 := \frac{-7^4 + 3^6 - 2^6 + 4^7}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$7325 := \frac{7^1 + 3^7 + 2^8 + 5^7}{7^0 + 3^0 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$7325 := \frac{7^1 + 3^7 + 2^8 + 5^7}{7^0 + 3^0 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$7326 := \frac{7^3 + 3^1 + 2^{17} + 6^5}{7^0 + 3^0 + 2^4 + 6^0}$$

$$7326 := \frac{7^3 + 3^1 + 2^{17} + 6^5}{7^0 + 3^0 + 2^4 + 6^0}$$

$$7327 := \frac{7^3 + 3^8 - 2^{14} + 7^5}{-7^0 - 3^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$7328 := \frac{7^3 + 3^2 + 2^{16} + 8^2}{7^0 + 3^1 + 2^2 + 8^0}$$

$$7328 := \frac{7^3 + 3^2 + 2^{16} + 8^2}{7^0 + 3^1 + 2^2 + 8^0}$$

$$7329 := \frac{7^3 + 3^0 + 2^{16} + 9^2}{7^0 + 3^1 + 2^2 + 9^0}$$

$$7330 := \frac{-7^7 - 3^{11} + 3^{14} + 0^0}{-7^4 + 3^6 + 3^7 + 0^0}$$

$$7332 := \frac{7^6 - 3^6 + 3^{10} - 2^0}{-7^0 - 3^0 + 3^3 - 2^0}$$

$$7333 := \frac{7^3 + 3^0 - 3^6 + 3^{10}}{7^0 + 3^0 + 3^1 + 3^1}$$

$$7334 := \frac{7^4 - 3^4 + 3^9 - 4^0}{-7^0 - 3^0 + 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7335 := \frac{7^3 + 3^5 + 3^{10} - 5^6}{7^0 + 3^0 + 3^1 + 5^0}$$

$$7336 := \frac{-7^4 - 3^2 + 3^{13} - 6^0}{7^2 + 3^4 + 3^4 + 6^1}$$

$$7337 := \frac{-7^0 - 3^2 + 3^{10} - 7^3}{7^0 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 7^0}$$

$$7338 := \frac{7^2 + 3^6 + 3^8 - 8^0}{7^0 + 3^0 - 3^2 + 8^1}$$

$$7339 := \frac{-7^3 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 9^5}{7^0 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 9^0}$$

$$7340 := \frac{7^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 0^1}{7^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$$

$$7341 := \frac{7^7 - 3^8 + 4^9 + 1^0}{7^0 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 1^0}$$

$$7342 := \frac{7^7 + 3^3 + 4^3 + 2^{20}}{7^1 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 2^2}$$

$$7342 := \frac{7^7 + 3^3 + 4^3 + 2^{20}}{7^1 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 2^2}$$

$$7343 := \frac{7^3 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 3^{10}}{7^1 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 3^0}$$

$$7344 := \frac{7^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 4^9}{7^0 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 4^2}$$

$7344 := \frac{7^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 4^9}{7^0 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 4^2}$	$7355 := \frac{7^6 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 5^2}{7^0 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 5^1}$	$7369 := \frac{7^5 + 3^{17} + 6^8 + 9^1}{7^5 + 3^1 + 6^3 + 9^3}$
$7345 := \frac{7^4 + 3^1 + 4^{10} + 5^9}{7^0 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^3}$	$7355 := \frac{7^6 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 5^2}{7^0 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 5^1}$	$7369 := \frac{7^5 + 3^{17} + 6^8 + 9^1}{7^5 + 3^1 + 6^3 + 9^3}$
$7345 := \frac{7^4 + 3^1 + 4^{10} + 5^9}{7^0 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^3}$	$7357 := \frac{7^2 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 7^6}{7^0 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 7^1}$	$7369 := \frac{-7^7 - 3^7 + 6^7 + 9^7}{-7^3 - 3^3 + 6^3 + 9^3}$
$7346 := \frac{7^4 + 3^{11} + 4^6 + 6^1}{7^1 + 3^0 + 4^2 + 6^0}$	$7357 := \frac{7^2 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 7^6}{7^0 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 7^1}$	$7370 := \frac{-7^0 + 3^{13} - 7^4 - 0^0}{7^0 - 3^7 + 7^4 + 0^0}$
$7346 := \frac{7^4 + 3^{11} + 4^6 + 6^1}{7^1 + 3^0 + 4^2 + 6^0}$	$7358 := \frac{7^6 + 3^4 - 5^0 - 8^0}{7^0 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 8^0}$	$7373 := \frac{7^2 + 3^3 + 7^6 + 3^5}{7^1 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 3^0}$
$7347 := \frac{7^0 + 3^5 + 4^8 + 7^3}{7^0 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^0}$	$7359 := \frac{7^6 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 9^2}{7^0 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 9^1}$	$7373 := \frac{7^2 + 3^3 + 7^6 + 3^5}{7^1 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 3^0}$
$7347 := \frac{7^0 + 3^5 + 4^8 + 7^3}{7^0 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^0}$	$7359 := \frac{7^6 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 9^2}{7^0 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 9^1}$	$7374 := \frac{-7^1 + 3^{10} - 7^2 - 4^0}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 4^0}$
$7348 := \frac{7^6 + 3^1 + 4^8 + 8^3}{7^1 + 3^0 + 4^2 + 8^0}$	$7361 := \frac{-7^9 - 3^{15} + 6^{10} + 1^0}{7^2 + 3^6 + 6^1 - 1^0}$	$7375 := \frac{7^3 + 3^1 + 7^6 + 5^1}{7^0 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 5^1}$
$7348 := \frac{7^6 + 3^1 + 4^8 + 8^3}{7^1 + 3^0 + 4^2 + 8^0}$	$7362 := \frac{7^6 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 2^7}{7^0 + 3^0 + 6^1 + 2^3}$	$7375 := \frac{7^3 + 3^1 + 7^6 + 5^1}{7^0 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 5^1}$
$7349 := \frac{7^0 + 3^{11} + 4^2 + 9^4}{7^1 + 3^0 + 4^2 + 9^0}$	$7362 := \frac{7^6 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 2^7}{7^0 + 3^0 + 6^1 + 2^3}$	$7376 := \frac{7^1 + 3^{10} - 7^2 + 6^0}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 6^0}$
$7349 := \frac{7^0 + 3^{11} + 4^2 + 9^4}{7^1 + 3^0 + 4^2 + 9^0}$	$7363 := \frac{7^3 + 3^5 + 6^3 + 3^8}{-7^0 - 3^0 + 6^1 - 3^1}$	$7377 := \frac{7^1 + 3^{10} + 7^3 + 7^6}{7^1 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 7^1}$
$7350 := \frac{7^0 + 3^{13} + 5^4 + 0^0}{-7^0 + 3^5 - 5^2 + 0^1}$	$7364 := \frac{7^5 + 3^{10} - 6^6 + 4^4}{7^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$	$7377 := \frac{7^1 + 3^{10} + 7^3 + 7^6}{7^1 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 7^1}$
$7351 := \frac{7^6 - 3^2 - 5^2 + 1^0}{7^1 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 1^1}$	$7365 := \frac{7^3 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 5^7}{7^0 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 5^0}$	$7378 := \frac{7^2 + 3^9 + 7^4 + 8^0}{7^0 + 3^0 - 7^1 + 8^1}$
$7352 := \frac{7^6 + 3^2 - 5^2 - 2^0}{7^0 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 2^0}$	$7365 := \frac{7^3 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 5^7}{7^0 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 5^0}$	$7379 := \frac{-7^0 - 3^2 - 7^1 + 9^5}{-7^0 - 3^0 + 7^0 + 9^1}$
$7353 := \frac{7^4 + 3^{12} + 5^{11} + 3^{13}}{7^0 + 3^5 + 5^3 + 3^8}$	$7366 := \frac{7^2 - 3^5 - 6^3 + 6^5}{-7^0 - 3^1 - 6^0 + 6^1}$	$7380 := \frac{-7^0 + 3^{10} - 8^1 + 0^1}{-7^0 + 3^0 + 8^1 + 0^1}$
$7353 := \frac{7^4 + 3^{12} + 5^{11} + 3^{13}}{7^0 + 3^5 + 5^3 + 3^8}$	$7367 := \frac{-7^4 - 3^4 + 6^5 + 7^5}{-7^0 - 3^0 + 6^1 - 7^0}$	$7381 := \frac{-7^0 + 3^{10} - 8^0 + 1^0}{-7^0 + 3^2 - 8^0 + 1^0}$
$7354 := \frac{7^6 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 4^0}{7^0 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 4^0}$	$7368 := \frac{7^3 + 3^8 + 6^7 + 8^3}{7^0 + 3^0 + 6^2 + 8^0}$	$7382 := \frac{7^7 + 3^{10} + 8^1 + 2^{15}}{7^0 + 3^3 + 8^2 + 2^5}$
$7354 := \frac{7^6 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 4^0}{7^0 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 4^0}$	$7368 := \frac{7^3 + 3^8 + 6^7 + 8^3}{7^0 + 3^0 + 6^2 + 8^0}$	$7382 := \frac{7^7 + 3^{10} + 8^1 + 2^{15}}{7^0 + 3^3 + 8^2 + 2^5}$

$$7383 := \frac{7^4 + 3^0 + 8^2 + 3^9}{-7^0 - 3^0 + 8^1 - 3^1}$$

$$7384 := \frac{7^7 + 3^{10} + 8^5 + 4^4}{7^2 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 4^3}$$

$$7384 := \frac{7^7 + 3^{10} + 8^5 + 4^4}{7^2 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 4^3}$$

$$7385 := \frac{7^7 + 3^{11} + 8^6 + 5^0}{7^0 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 5^2}$$

$$7385 := \frac{7^7 + 3^{11} + 8^6 + 5^0}{7^0 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 5^2}$$

$$7386 := \frac{7^6 + 3^2 + 8^3 + 6^1}{7^0 + 3^0 + 8^1 + 6^1}$$

$$7386 := \frac{7^6 + 3^2 + 8^3 + 6^1}{7^0 + 3^0 + 8^1 + 6^1}$$

$$7387 := \frac{7^3 + 3^{11} + 8^6 + 7^7}{7^2 + 3^2 + 8^2 + 7^2}$$

$$7387 := \frac{7^3 + 3^{11} + 8^6 + 7^7}{7^2 + 3^2 + 8^2 + 7^2}$$

$$7388 := \frac{7^2 + 3^3 + 8^4 + 8^5}{-7^0 - 3^0 - 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$7389 := \frac{7^3 - 3^3 + 8^3 + 9^4}{-7^0 + 3^0 - 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$7390 := \frac{7^0 + 3^3 + 9^8 + 0^0}{-7^1 - 3^6 + 9^4 + 0^1}$$

$$7391 := \frac{-7^0 + 3^4 + 9^5 - 1^0}{-7^0 - 3^0 + 9^1 + 1^0}$$

$$7392 := \frac{7^1 + 3^4 + 9^5 - 2^0}{-7^0 - 3^0 + 9^1 + 2^0}$$

$$7393 := \frac{7^6 - 3^2 - 9^2 + 3^6}{7^0 + 3^1 + 9^1 + 3^1}$$

$$7395 := \frac{-7^1 + 3^5 + 9^5 - 5^3}{7^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 5^1}$$

$$7396 := \frac{7^3 + 3^6 + 9^6 - 6^0}{-7^0 - 3^2 + 9^2 + 6^0}$$

$$7397 := \frac{7^0 - 3^3 + 9^3 + 7^6}{7^1 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$7398 := \frac{7^6 - 3^2 + 9^3 - 8^0}{-7^0 + 3^2 + 9^1 - 8^0}$$

$$7399 := \frac{7^8 + 3^0 + 9^4 + 9^5}{7^2 + 3^0 + 9^1 + 9^3}$$

$$7399 := \frac{7^8 + 3^0 + 9^4 + 9^5}{7^2 + 3^0 + 9^1 + 9^3}$$

$$7402 := \frac{7^3 + 4^{10} + 0^0 - 2^{17}}{-7^0 - 4^1 + 0^0 + 2^7}$$

$$7403 := \frac{-7^9 + 4^7 + 0^1 + 3^{16}}{7^3 - 4^1 + 0^1 + 3^3}$$

$$7405 := \frac{7^6 + 4^2 + 0^1 + 5^6}{7^0 + 4^2 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$7405 := \frac{7^6 + 4^2 + 0^1 + 5^6}{7^0 + 4^2 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$7406 := \frac{7^7 + 4^2 - 0^0 + 6^7}{7^2 + 4^3 + 0^1 + 6^2}$$

$$7407 := \frac{-7^3 - 4^5 + 0^0 + 7^7}{-7^0 + 4^3 - 0^0 + 7^2}$$

$$7408 := \frac{-7^6 - 4^7 + 0^0 + 8^7}{7^0 + 4^4 + 0^1 + 8^1}$$

$$7412 := \frac{7^5 + 4^3 + 1^0 - 2^{11}}{-7^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 2^0}$$

$$7413 := \frac{7^7 + 4^3 + 1^0 + 3^{11}}{7^2 + 4^1 + 1^0 + 3^4}$$

$$7413 := \frac{7^7 + 4^3 + 1^0 + 3^{11}}{7^2 + 4^1 + 1^0 + 3^4}$$

$$7416 := \frac{-7^3 - 4^2 - 1^0 + 6^5}{-7^0 + 4^1 - 1^0 - 6^0}$$

$$7417 := \frac{-7^0 - 4^4 + 1^0 + 7^7}{-7^0 + 4^3 - 1^0 + 7^2}$$

$$7419 := \frac{7^8 + 4^3 + 1^0 + 9^5}{-7^1 + 4^3 - 1^0 + 9^3}$$

$$7421 := \frac{7^6 + 4^3 + 2^{10} - 1^0}{7^1 + 4^1 + 2^2 + 1^0}$$

$$7422 := \frac{7^7 - 4^0 - 2^{18} - 2^{19}}{7^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$7423 := \frac{7^0 + 4^6 + 2^{13} + 3^{14}}{7^2 + 4^1 + 2^9 + 3^4}$$

$$7423 := \frac{7^0 + 4^6 + 2^{13} + 3^{14}}{7^2 + 4^1 + 2^9 + 3^4}$$

$$7424 := \frac{-7^0 + 4^0 + 2^8 + 4^{11}}{7^2 + 4^1 + 2^8 + 4^4}$$

$$7425 := \frac{7^6 + 4^5 + 2^1 + 5^3}{7^1 + 4^1 + 2^2 + 5^0}$$

$$7425 := \frac{7^6 + 4^5 + 2^1 + 5^3}{7^1 + 4^1 + 2^2 + 5^0}$$

$$7426 := \frac{7^0 + 4^0 + 2^{16} + 6^4}{7^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 6^1}$$

$$7426 := \frac{7^0 + 4^0 + 2^{16} + 6^4}{7^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 6^1}$$

$$7427 := \frac{-7^4 - 4^3 + 2^9 + 7^5}{-7^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$7429 := \frac{-7^0 + 4^4 + 2^7 + 9^5}{7^0 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$7432 := \frac{7^7 + 4^7 + 3^8 + 2^{13}}{7^0 + 4^0 + 3^4 + 2^5}$$

$$7433 := \frac{7^7 + 4^7 + 3^0 + 3^0}{7^0 + 4^1 + 3^3 + 3^4}$$

$$7433 := \frac{7^7 + 4^7 + 3^0 + 3^0}{7^0 + 4^1 + 3^3 + 3^4}$$

$$7434 := \frac{7^3 + 4^5 + 3^1 + 4^8}{7^0 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 4^1}$$

$$7434 := \frac{7^3 + 4^5 + 3^1 + 4^8}{7^0 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 4^1}$$

$$7435 := \frac{7^9 + 4^2 + 3^{12} + 5^0}{7^2 + 4^6 + 3^6 + 5^4}$$

$$7435 := \frac{7^9 + 4^2 + 3^{12} + 5^0}{7^2 + 4^6 + 3^6 + 5^4}$$

$$7436 := \frac{-7^3 + 4^1 - 3^0 + 6^5}{-7^0 - 4^0 - 3^1 + 6^1}$$

$$7437 := \frac{7^1 + 4^{10} + 3^3 + 7^1}{7^0 + 4^3 + 3^3 + 7^2}$$

$$7437 := \frac{7^1 + 4^{10} + 3^3 + 7^1}{7^0 + 4^3 + 3^3 + 7^2}$$

$$7438 := \frac{7^3 + 4^{11} + 3^9 + 8^5}{7^2 + 4^0 + 3^2 + 8^3}$$

$$7438 := \frac{7^3 + 4^{11} + 3^9 + 8^5}{7^2 + 4^0 + 3^2 + 8^3}$$

$$7439 := \frac{7^5 - 4^5 - 3^3 + 9^4}{-7^0 + 4^1 - 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$7440 := \frac{-7^6 - 4^{10} + 4^{11} + 0^0}{7^3 - 4^0 + 4^3 + 0^0}$$

$$7442 := \frac{-7^0 - 4^0 + 4^6 + 2^{19}}{7^0 + 4^1 + 4^3 + 2^1}$$

$$7443 := \frac{7^0 + 4^6 + 4^8 + 3^9}{7^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 3^2}$$

$$7443 := \frac{7^0 + 4^6 + 4^8 + 3^9}{7^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 3^2}$$

$$7444 := \frac{7^6 - 4^0 - 4^1 - 4^8}{7^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7445 := \frac{7^6 + 4^0 - 4^8 + 5^0}{7^0 + 4^0 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$7446 := \frac{-7^5 - 4^0 - 4^3 + 6^6}{7^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$7447 := \frac{7^4 + 4^6 + 4^{10} + 7^4}{7^1 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 7^1}$$

$$7447 := \frac{7^4 + 4^6 + 4^{10} + 7^4}{7^1 + 4^3 + 4^3 + 7^1}$$

$$7448 := \frac{7^1 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 8^0}{7^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 8^1}$$

$$7448 := \frac{7^1 + 4^7 + 4^8 + 8^0}{7^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 8^1}$$

$$7449 := \frac{7^6 + 4^{11} + 4^{12} + 9^8}{7^0 + 4^5 + 4^5 + 9^4}$$

$$7449 := \frac{7^6 + 4^{11} + 4^{12} + 9^8}{7^0 + 4^5 + 4^5 + 9^4}$$

$$7452 := \frac{7^3 + 4^5 + 5^5 + 2^{15}}{7^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$7452 := \frac{7^3 + 4^5 + 5^5 + 2^{15}}{7^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$7453 := \frac{7^7 + 4^3 + 5^7 + 3^4}{7^2 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 3^1}$$

$$7453 := \frac{7^7 + 4^3 + 5^7 + 3^4}{7^2 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 3^1}$$

$$7454 := \frac{7^2 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 4^8}{7^0 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 4^1}$$

$$7454 := \frac{7^2 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 4^8}{7^0 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 4^1}$$

$$7455 := \frac{7^4 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 5^7}{7^1 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7455 := \frac{7^4 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 5^7}{7^1 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7456 := \frac{7^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 6^7}{7^0 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 6^2}$$

$$7456 := \frac{7^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 6^7}{7^0 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 6^2}$$

$$7457 := \frac{7^3 + 4^{10} + 5^4 + 7^5}{7^0 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^0}$$

$$7457 := \frac{7^3 + 4^{10} + 5^4 + 7^5}{7^0 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^0}$$

$$7458 := \frac{7^1 + 4^8 + 5^3 + 8^7}{7^0 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 8^1}$$

$$7458 := \frac{7^1 + 4^8 + 5^3 + 8^7}{7^0 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 8^1}$$

$$7459 := \frac{-7^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4}{-7^0 + 4^1 - 5^0 - 9^0}$$

$$7460 := \frac{7^1 + 4^{12} + 6^5 + 0^0}{7^4 + 4^3 - 6^3 + 0^0}$$

$$7461 := \frac{-7^5 - 4^1 + 6^6 - 1^0}{7^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$7462 := \frac{-7^5 + 4^0 + 6^6 - 2^1}{7^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$7463 := \frac{7^8 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 3^0}{7^1 + 4^0 + 6^2 + 3^6}$$

$$7463 := \frac{7^8 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 3^0}{7^1 + 4^0 + 6^2 + 3^6}$$

$$7464 := \frac{7^3 + 4^0 + 6^4 + 4^8}{7^0 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 4^0}$$

$$7464 := \frac{7^3 + 4^0 + 6^4 + 4^8}{7^0 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 4^0}$$

$$7465 := \frac{7^1 + 4^0 + 6^8 + 5^0}{7^1 + 4^0 + 6^3 + 5^0}$$

$$7465 := \frac{7^1 + 4^0 + 6^8 + 5^0}{7^1 + 4^0 + 6^3 + 5^0}$$

$$7466 := \frac{-7^5 + 4^2 - 6^0 + 6^6}{7^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$7467 := \frac{7^5 + 4^3 + 6^7 + 7^5}{7^0 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$7467 := \frac{7^5 + 4^3 + 6^7 + 7^5}{7^0 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$7468 := \frac{7^1 + 4^0 + 6^9 + 8^4}{7^2 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^0}$$

$$7468 := \frac{7^1 + 4^0 + 6^9 + 8^4}{7^2 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^0}$$

$$7469 := \frac{7^6 + 4^1 + 6^6 + 9^1}{-7^0 - 4^1 + 6^2 - 9^1}$$

$$7470 := \frac{7^5 + 4^1 + 7^6 + 0^1}{7^1 + 4^1 + 7^1 + 0^1}$$

$$7470 := \frac{7^5 + 4^1 + 7^6 + 0^1}{7^1 + 4^1 + 7^1 + 0^1}$$

$$7472 := \frac{-7^2 + 4^5 + 7^4 + 2^{12}}{-7^0 - 4^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$7473 := \frac{7^3 + 4^7 + 7^8 + 3^{13}}{7^0 + 4^4 + 7^0 + 3^6}$$

$$7473 := \frac{7^3 + 4^7 + 7^8 + 3^{13}}{7^0 + 4^4 + 7^0 + 3^6}$$

$$7474 := \frac{7^8 + 4^{11} + 7^8 + 4^{11}}{7^1 + 4^0 + 7^4 + 4^4}$$

$$7474 := \frac{7^8 + 4^{11} + 7^8 + 4^{11}}{7^1 + 4^0 + 7^4 + 4^4}$$

$7475 := \frac{7^1 + 4^8 + 7^5 - 5^3}{7^0 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 5^1}$	$7492 := \frac{7^1 + 4^3 + 9^2 + 2^{19}}{7^0 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 2^6}$	$7522 := \frac{7^1 + 5^8 + 2^8 + 2^8}{7^1 + 5^1 + 2^3 + 2^5}$
$7476 := \frac{7^1 + 4^6 + 7^2 + 6^7}{-7^0 + 4^1 - 7^0 + 6^2}$	$7493 := \frac{7^5 + 4^8 - 9^0 + 3^4}{-7^0 + 4^1 - 9^0 + 3^2}$	$7523 := \frac{7^8 + 5^9 + 2^{13} + 3^1}{7^0 + 5^0 + 2^{10} + 3^0}$
$7477 := \frac{-7^5 + 4^{11} + 7^7 + 7^7}{7^2 + 4^5 + 7^2 - 7^3}$	$7494 := \frac{7^5 + 4^5 + 9^4 + 4^8}{7^0 + 4^0 + 9^1 + 4^0}$	$7523 := \frac{7^8 + 5^9 + 2^{13} + 3^1}{7^0 + 5^0 + 2^{10} + 3^0}$
$7478 := \frac{-7^1 - 4^3 - 7^3 + 8^6}{7^0 - 4^2 + 7^2 + 8^0}$	$7494 := \frac{7^5 + 4^5 + 9^4 + 4^8}{7^0 + 4^0 + 9^1 + 4^0}$	$7524 := \frac{7^1 + 5^3 + 2^{11} + 4^8}{7^0 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 4^0}$
$7479 := \frac{7^0 + 4^3 + 7^7 + 9^4}{7^1 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^2}$	$7495 := \frac{7^5 + 4^7 + 9^7 + 5^5}{7^0 + 4^2 + 9^0 + 5^4}$	$7524 := \frac{7^1 + 5^3 + 2^{11} + 4^8}{7^0 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 4^0}$
$7479 := \frac{7^0 + 4^3 + 7^7 + 9^4}{7^1 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^2}$	$7495 := \frac{7^5 + 4^7 + 9^7 + 5^5}{7^0 + 4^2 + 9^0 + 5^4}$	$7525 := \frac{7^2 + 5^4 + 2^0 + 5^8}{7^0 + 5^2 + 2^0 + 5^2}$
$7480 := \frac{7^5 + 4^8 - 8^2 + 0^0}{7^0 + 4^0 + 8^1 + 0^0}$	$7496 := \frac{-7^3 + 4^3 - 9^0 + 6^5}{-7^0 - 4^0 + 9^1 - 6^1}$	$7525 := \frac{7^2 + 5^4 + 2^0 + 5^8}{7^0 + 5^2 + 2^0 + 5^2}$
$7482 := \frac{7^6 + 4^2 - 8^0 + 2^{11}}{7^1 + 4^1 + 8^0 + 2^2}$	$7497 := \frac{7^3 + 4^5 - 9^4 + 7^6}{7^0 + 4^1 + 9^1 + 7^0}$	$7526 := \frac{7^4 + 5^3 + 2^{19} + 6^1}{7^0 + 5^0 + 2^5 + 6^2}$
$7483 := \frac{7^3 + 4^8 + 8^7 - 3^{13}}{7^0 + 4^3 + 8^1 + 3^1}$	$7498 := \frac{7^5 - 4^7 + 9^5 + 8^3}{-7^0 - 4^0 + 9^1 + 8^0}$	$7526 := \frac{7^4 + 5^3 + 2^{19} + 6^1}{7^0 + 5^0 + 2^5 + 6^2}$
$7484 := \frac{-7^7 - 4^0 - 8^3 + 4^{10}}{-7^0 + 4^2 - 8^0 + 4^2}$	$7499 := \frac{7^0 + 4^1 - 9^4 + 9^5}{7^0 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 9^0}$	$7527 := \frac{7^5 + 5^9 + 2^{19} + 7^6}{7^0 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 7^3}$
$7485 := \frac{7^0 - 4^7 + 8^1 + 5^8}{7^0 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 5^2}$	$7504 := \frac{7^4 - 5^8 + 0^1 + 4^{10}}{-7^0 + 5^2 + 0^1 + 4^3}$	$7527 := \frac{7^5 + 5^9 + 2^{19} + 7^6}{7^0 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 7^3}$
$7486 := \frac{7^6 - 4^8 - 8^0 + 6^5}{-7^0 + 4^1 - 8^0 + 6^1}$	$7505 := \frac{7^2 - 5^5 + 0^0 + 5^7}{7^1 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 5^0}$	$7528 := \frac{7^5 + 5^2 + 2^{17} + 8^5}{7^1 + 5^0 + 2^3 + 8^1}$
$7487 := \frac{-7^2 - 4^0 + 8^6 - 7^2}{7^0 - 4^2 + 8^0 + 7^2}$	$7506 := \frac{-7^3 + 5^6 + 0^1 - 6^5}{-7^0 + 5^0 + 0^1 + 6^0}$	$7528 := \frac{7^5 + 5^2 + 2^{17} + 8^5}{7^1 + 5^0 + 2^3 + 8^1}$
$7488 := \frac{-7^0 + 4^0 - 8^2 + 8^6}{7^2 - 4^2 + 8^0 + 8^0}$	$7512 := \frac{-7^0 + 5^8 - 1^0 + 2^0}{7^2 + 5^0 + 1^0 + 2^0}$	$7529 := \frac{7^8 + 5^5 + 2^8 + 9^4}{7^0 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 9^3}$
$7489 := \frac{-7^2 + 4^9 + 8^6 - 9^1}{7^0 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^0}$	$7513 := \frac{7^2 + 5^8 + 1^0 + 3^0}{7^2 + 5^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$	$7529 := \frac{7^8 + 5^5 + 2^8 + 9^4}{7^0 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 9^3}$
$7490 := \frac{7^1 + 4^9 - 9^0 + 0^1}{7^2 - 4^1 - 9^1 - 0^0}$	$7513 := \frac{7^2 + 5^8 + 1^0 + 3^0}{7^2 + 5^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$	$7530 := \frac{7^3 + 5^4 + 3^8 + 0^0}{-7^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$
$7491 := \frac{7^2 + 4^9 - 9^1 + 1^0}{7^2 - 4^1 - 9^1 - 1^0}$	$7520 := \frac{7^6 - 5^4 + 2^{20} + 0^1}{7^0 + 5^2 + 2^7 + 0^0}$	$7532 := \frac{-7^3 + 5^7 + 3^{13} - 2^0}{7^3 - 5^3 + 3^1 + 2^0}$
$7492 := \frac{7^1 + 4^3 + 9^2 + 2^{19}}{7^0 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 2^6}$	$7522 := \frac{7^1 + 5^8 + 2^8 + 2^8}{7^1 + 5^1 + 2^3 + 2^5}$	$7533 := \frac{7^6 + 5^7 + 3^1 + 3^4}{7^1 + 5^0 + 3^2 + 3^2}$

$$7533 := \frac{7^6 + 5^7 + 3^1 + 3^4}{7^1 + 5^0 + 3^2 + 3^2}$$

$$7534 := \frac{7^6 - 5^2 - 3^9 + 4^0}{7^0 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 4^1}$$

$$7535 := \frac{7^4 + 5^2 + 3^{10} + 5^8}{7^0 + 5^2 + 3^2 + 5^2}$$

$$7535 := \frac{7^4 + 5^2 + 3^{10} + 5^8}{7^0 + 5^2 + 3^2 + 5^2}$$

$$7536 := \frac{7^6 + 5^0 - 3^9 + 6^0}{7^0 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 6^1}$$

$$7537 := \frac{7^5 + 5^1 + 3^{17} + 7^6}{7^3 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 7^5}$$

$$7537 := \frac{7^5 + 5^1 + 3^{17} + 7^6}{7^3 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 7^5}$$

$$7538 := \frac{7^8 + 5^7 + 3^8 + 8^0}{7^2 - 5^0 + 3^6 - 8^0}$$

$$7539 := \frac{7^4 + 5^3 + 3^{10} + 9^5}{7^0 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7539 := \frac{7^4 + 5^3 + 3^{10} + 9^5}{7^0 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7541 := \frac{-7^0 + 5^9 - 4^1 - 1^0}{7^0 + 5^0 + 4^4 + 1^0}$$

$$7542 := \frac{7^5 + 5^7 + 4^4 + 2^{17}}{7^0 + 5^1 + 4^2 + 2^3}$$

$$7542 := \frac{7^5 + 5^7 + 4^4 + 2^{17}}{7^0 + 5^1 + 4^2 + 2^3}$$

$$7543 := \frac{7^6 - 5^5 - 4^7 - 3^4}{7^0 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 3^1}$$

$$7544 := \frac{7^5 + 5^4 + 4^2 + 4^8}{7^0 + 5^1 + 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7544 := \frac{7^5 + 5^4 + 4^2 + 4^8}{7^0 + 5^1 + 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7545 := \frac{7^2 + 5^1 + 4^{10} + 5^3}{7^2 + 5^0 + 4^3 + 5^2}$$

$$7545 := \frac{7^2 + 5^1 + 4^{10} + 5^3}{7^2 + 5^0 + 4^3 + 5^2}$$

$$7546 := \frac{7^5 + 5^8 + 4^2 + 6^2}{7^0 + 5^0 + 4^2 + 6^2}$$

$$7546 := \frac{7^5 + 5^8 + 4^2 + 6^2}{7^0 + 5^0 + 4^2 + 6^2}$$

$$7547 := \frac{7^2 + 5^4 + 4^8 + 7^5}{7^0 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 7^0}$$

$$7547 := \frac{7^2 + 5^4 + 4^8 + 7^5}{7^0 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 7^0}$$

$$7548 := \frac{7^3 + 5^5 - 4^2 + 8^4}{-7^0 - 5^0 + 4^1 - 8^0}$$

$$7549 := \frac{7^6 + 5^5 + 4^0 + 9^1}{7^0 + 5^1 + 4^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7549 := \frac{7^6 + 5^5 + 4^0 + 9^1}{7^0 + 5^1 + 4^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7550 := \frac{7^6 + 5^6 + 5^7 + 0^0}{7^0 + 5^0 + 5^2 + 0^0}$$

$$7550 := \frac{7^6 + 5^6 + 5^7 + 0^0}{7^0 + 5^0 + 5^2 + 0^0}$$

$$7553 := \frac{7^6 - 5^3 + 5^7 + 3^6}{7^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 + 3^2}$$

$$7554 := \frac{7^5 - 5^0 + 5^{10} - 4^0}{7^2 + 5^4 + 5^4 - 4^1}$$

$$7556 := \frac{7^6 - 5^2 + 5^{10} - 6^0}{7^5 + 5^3 - 5^6 + 6^0}$$

$$7557 := \frac{7^2 - 5^5 + 5^9 - 7^3}{7^0 + 5^3 + 5^3 + 7^1}$$

$$7559 := \frac{-7^4 - 5^3 + 5^7 - 9^1}{7^1 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$7562 := \frac{7^5 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 2^{16}}{7^0 + 5^0 + 6^1 + 2^2}$$

$$7562 := \frac{7^5 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 2^{16}}{7^0 + 5^0 + 6^1 + 2^2}$$

$$7563 := \frac{7^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 3^{11}}{7^0 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 3^0}$$

$$7563 := \frac{7^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 3^{11}}{7^0 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 3^0}$$

$$7564 := \frac{7^2 + 5^7 + 6^1 + 4^8}{7^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 4^2}$$

$$7564 := \frac{7^2 + 5^7 + 6^1 + 4^8}{7^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 4^2}$$

$$7565 := \frac{7^2 + 5^5 + 6^6 + 5^5}{-7^0 + 5^0 + 6^1 + 5^0}$$

$$7566 := \frac{7^1 + 5^1 + 6^7 + 6^7}{7^0 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 6^2}$$

$$7566 := \frac{7^1 + 5^1 + 6^7 + 6^7}{7^0 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 6^2}$$

$$7567 := \frac{-7^0 - 5^1 + 6^7 + 7^2}{-7^0 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$7568 := \frac{-7^4 + 5^7 - 6^2 - 8^1}{7^1 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$7569 := \frac{-7^0 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^2}{-7^0 - 5^0 - 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$7572 := \frac{-7^5 - 5^7 + 7^6 - 2^0}{-7^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$7573 := \frac{7^7 + 5^9 + 7^7 + 3^9}{7^0 + 5^3 + 7^3 + 3^2}$$

$$7573 := \frac{7^7 + 5^9 + 7^7 + 3^9}{7^0 + 5^3 + 7^3 + 3^2}$$

$$7575 := \frac{-7^1 - 5^3 - 7^3 + 5^6}{-7^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7576 := \frac{-7^4 + 5^{10} - 7^7 - 6^0}{-7^0 - 5^6 + 7^5 - 6^0}$$

$$7577 := \frac{7^4 - 5^6 + 7^5 + 7^6}{7^0 + 5^0 + 7^1 + 7^1}$$

$$7579 := \frac{-7^4 + 5^7 + 7^5 + 9^5}{7^1 + 5^1 + 7^1 + 9^0}$$

$$7580 := \frac{7^6 - 5^6 + 8^4 + 0^1}{7^0 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 0^1}$$

$$7581 := \frac{-7^0 - 5^6 + 8^8 + 1^0}{7^4 - 5^3 - 8^2 - 1^0}$$

$$7582 := \frac{7^7 + 5^8 + 8^6 + 2^{17}}{7^1 + 5^3 + 8^2 + 2^4}$$

$$7582 := \frac{7^7 + 5^8 + 8^6 + 2^{17}}{7^1 + 5^3 + 8^2 + 2^4}$$

$$7583 := \frac{7^5 - 5^2 - 8^0 + 3^{10}}{7^0 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 3^1}$$

$$7584 := \frac{7^5 + 5^2 + 8^5 - 4^6}{7^0 + 5^0 + 8^1 - 4^1}$$

$$7585 := \frac{7^{11} + 5^0 + 8^8 + 5^3}{7^1 + 5^3 + 8^6 + 5^4}$$

$$7585 := \frac{7^{11} + 5^0 + 8^8 + 5^3}{7^1 + 5^3 + 8^6 + 5^4}$$

$$7586 := \frac{7^0 + 5^0 + 8^4 + 6^9}{7^1 + 5^2 + 8^0 + 6^4}$$

$$7586 := \frac{7^0 + 5^0 + 8^4 + 6^9}{7^1 + 5^2 + 8^0 + 6^4}$$

$$7587 := \frac{-7^3 + 5^0 + 8^6 - 7^6}{-7^0 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$7588 := \frac{-7^0 + 5^6 + 8^2 - 8^3}{-7^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$7589 := \frac{7^6 - 5^6 - 8^4 + 9^3}{-7^0 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 9^0}$$

$$7592 := \frac{-7^4 + 5^8 + 9^4 - 2^0}{7^2 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$7593 := \frac{7^0 + 5^3 + 9^2 + 3^{13}}{7^0 + 5^3 + 9^2 + 3^1}$$

$$7593 := \frac{7^0 + 5^3 + 9^2 + 3^{13}}{7^0 + 5^3 + 9^2 + 3^1}$$

$$7594 := \frac{7^6 + 5^5 + 9^3 + 4^0}{7^0 + 5^1 + 9^1 + 4^0}$$

$$7594 := \frac{7^6 + 5^5 + 9^3 + 4^0}{7^0 + 5^1 + 9^1 + 4^0}$$

$$7595 := \frac{7^6 - 5^5 + 9^4 + 5^6}{7^1 + 5^0 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$7596 := \frac{-7^0 + 5^{11} + 9^4 - 6^0}{-7^0 - 5^3 + 9^4 - 6^1}$$

$$7597 := \frac{7^2 + 5^5 + 9^3 + 7^6}{7^0 + 5^1 + 9^1 + 7^0}$$

$$7597 := \frac{7^2 + 5^5 + 9^3 + 7^6}{7^0 + 5^1 + 9^1 + 7^0}$$

$$7598 := \frac{7^5 + 5^3 + 9^5 - 8^0}{7^1 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$7599 := \frac{7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5}{7^1 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$7599 := \frac{7^5 + 5^3 + 9^1 + 9^5}{7^1 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$7603 := \frac{7^5 + 6^5 + 0^0 + 3^{10}}{7^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 3^2}$$

$$7603 := \frac{7^5 + 6^5 + 0^0 + 3^{10}}{7^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 3^2}$$

$$7604 := \frac{7^5 + 6^9 + 0^0 + 4^9}{7^0 + 6^4 + 0^0 + 4^3}$$

$$7604 := \frac{7^5 + 6^9 + 0^0 + 4^9}{7^0 + 6^4 + 0^0 + 4^3}$$

$$7608 := \frac{7^3 + 6^5 + 0^0 - 8^3}{-7^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 8^0}$$

$$7609 := \frac{7^5 + 6^7 - 0^0 + 9^1}{7^0 + 6^2 + 0^0 + 9^0}$$

$$7614 := \frac{7^8 + 6^1 + 1^0 + 4^{11}}{7^1 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7614 := \frac{7^8 + 6^1 + 1^0 + 4^{11}}{7^1 + 6^4 + 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7620 := \frac{-7^5 + 6^2 + 2^{17} - 0^0}{7^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 0^1}$$

$$7621 := \frac{7^7 + 6^2 - 2^9 + 1^0}{7^1 + 6^2 + 2^6 + 1^0}$$

$$7622 := \frac{7^5 + 6^0 + 2^{16} + 2^{17}}{7^1 + 6^0 + 2^2 + 2^4}$$

$$7622 := \frac{7^5 + 6^0 + 2^{16} + 2^{17}}{7^1 + 6^0 + 2^2 + 2^4}$$

$$7623 := \frac{7^4 + 6^3 + 2^{13} + 3^9}{7^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$7623 := \frac{7^4 + 6^3 + 2^{13} + 3^9}{7^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$7624 := \frac{7^7 + 6^0 + 2^{16} + 4^9}{7^0 + 6^1 + 2^7 + 4^2}$$

$$7624 := \frac{7^7 + 6^0 + 2^{16} + 4^9}{7^0 + 6^1 + 2^7 + 4^2}$$

$$7625 := \frac{-7^3 - 6^2 + 2^2 + 5^6}{-7^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7626 := \frac{7^7 + 6^3 - 2^0 - 6^5}{7^0 + 6^1 + 2^6 + 6^2}$$

$$7627 := \frac{7^5 + 6^0 + 2^{16} + 7^5}{7^0 + 6^0 + 2^2 + 7^1}$$

$$7627 := \frac{7^5 + 6^0 + 2^{16} + 7^5}{7^0 + 6^0 + 2^2 + 7^1}$$

$$7628 := \frac{7^7 + 6^3 + 2^0 + 8^2}{7^1 + 6^2 + 2^0 + 8^2}$$

$$7628 := \frac{7^7 + 6^3 + 2^0 + 8^2}{7^1 + 6^2 + 2^0 + 8^2}$$

$$7629 := \frac{7^6 + 6^6 + 2^{19} + 9^5}{7^1 + 6^1 + 2^2 + 9^2}$$

$$7629 := \frac{7^6 + 6^6 + 2^{19} + 9^5}{7^1 + 6^1 + 2^2 + 9^2}$$

$$7630 := \frac{7^4 + 6^7 - 3^3 + 0^1}{-7^0 + 6^2 + 3^0 + 0^0}$$

$$7631 := \frac{7^4 + 6^7 + 3^2 + 1^0}{-7^0 + 6^2 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$7632 := \frac{7^6 + 6^2 + 3^9 + 2^3}{7^1 + 6^1 + 3^1 + 2^1}$$

$$7633 := \frac{7^4 + 6^7 + 3^1 + 3^4}{7^0 + 6^1 + 3^1 + 3^3}$$

$$7633 := \frac{7^4 + 6^7 + 3^1 + 3^4}{7^0 + 6^1 + 3^1 + 3^3}$$

$$7634 := \frac{-7^1 - 6^2 + 3^8 + 4^7}{-7^0 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7635 := \frac{7^8 + 6^9 + 3^1 + 5^3}{7^2 + 6^4 + 3^6 + 5^0}$$

$$7635 := \frac{7^8 + 6^9 + 3^1 + 5^3}{7^2 + 6^4 + 3^6 + 5^0}$$

$$7636 := \frac{7^2 - 6^3 + 3^3 + 6^5}{-7^0 - 6^0 - 3^1 + 6^1}$$

$$7637 := \frac{-7^4 + 6^5 + 3^6 + 7^5}{-7^0 + 6^1 - 3^0 - 7^0}$$

$$7638 := \frac{7^7 + 6^4 + 3^0 + 8^2}{7^1 + 6^2 + 3^0 + 8^2}$$

$$7638 := \frac{7^7 + 6^4 + 3^0 + 8^2}{7^1 + 6^2 + 3^0 + 8^2}$$

$$7639 := \frac{7^3 + 6^1 + 3^6 + 9^4}{-7^0 - 6^1 - 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7640 := \frac{-7^4 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 0^0}{-7^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$7642 := \frac{7^0 + 6^8 + 4^0 + 2^{20}}{7^0 + 6^2 + 4^3 + 2^8}$$

$$7642 := \frac{7^0 + 6^8 + 4^0 + 2^{20}}{7^0 + 6^2 + 4^3 + 2^8}$$

$$7643 := \frac{-7^0 + 6^1 + 4^8 - 3^9}{7^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 3^1}$$

$$7644 := \frac{7^8 - 6^0 + 4^5 - 4^9}{-7^2 + 6^0 - 4^4 + 4^5}$$

$$7645 := \frac{7^7 + 6^8 + 4^8 + 5^2}{7^2 + 6^1 + 4^4 + 5^2}$$

$$7645 := \frac{7^7 + 6^8 + 4^8 + 5^2}{7^2 + 6^1 + 4^4 + 5^2}$$

$$7646 := \frac{7^6 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 6^7}{7^2 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$7646 := \frac{7^6 + 6^1 + 4^0 + 6^7}{7^2 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$7647 := \frac{7^5 + 6^8 + 4^{12} + 7^5}{7^1 + 6^1 + 4^1 + 7^4}$$

$$7647 := \frac{7^5 + 6^8 + 4^{12} + 7^5}{7^1 + 6^1 + 4^1 + 7^4}$$

$$7648 := \frac{7^6 + 6^8 + 4^2 - 8^0}{7^1 + 6^3 + 4^1 + 8^1}$$

$$7649 := \frac{7^0 + 6^0 + 4^7 + 9^4}{-7^0 - 6^0 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$7650 := \frac{-7^0 + 6^5 - 5^3 + 0^1}{-7^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$7651 := \frac{-7^0 + 6^5 - 5^3 + 1^0}{7^0 - 6^1 + 5^1 + 1^0}$$

$$7652 := \frac{-7^0 + 6^5 + 5^1 - 2^7}{-7^0 - 6^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$7653 := \frac{7^{10} + 6^7 + 5^3 + 3^4}{7^3 + 6^4 + 5^6 + 3^9}$$

$$7653 := \frac{7^{10} + 6^7 + 5^3 + 3^4}{7^3 + 6^4 + 5^6 + 3^9}$$

$$7654 := \frac{-7^0 + 6^5 - 5^3 + 4^1}{-7^0 - 6^0 - 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7655 := \frac{7^2 + 6^7 + 5^3 + 5^5}{7^0 + 6^1 + 5^1 + 5^2}$$

$$7655 := \frac{7^2 + 6^7 + 5^3 + 5^5}{7^0 + 6^1 + 5^1 + 5^2}$$

$$7656 := \frac{-7^0 + 6^1 - 5^3 + 6^5}{-7^0 + 6^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$7657 := \frac{-7^0 + 6^5 - 5^3 + 7^1}{-7^0 - 6^1 + 5^0 + 7^1}$$

$$7658 := \frac{-7^0 + 6^5 - 5^3 + 8^1}{-7^0 - 6^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$7659 := \frac{-7^0 + 6^5 - 5^3 + 9^1}{-7^0 - 6^1 - 5^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7660 := \frac{7^6 + 6^5 + 6^9 - 0^0}{-7^0 + 6^2 + 6^4 + 0^0}$$

$$7662 := \frac{-7^2 - 6^0 + 6^5 - 2^6}{-7^0 - 6^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$7663 := \frac{7^8 + 6^5 + 6^7 + 3^{14}}{7^0 + 6^2 + 6^4 + 3^4}$$

$$7663 := \frac{7^8 + 6^5 + 6^7 + 3^{14}}{7^0 + 6^2 + 6^4 + 3^4}$$

$$7664 := \frac{-7^2 + 6^0 + 6^5 - 4^3}{-7^0 - 6^0 - 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7665 := \frac{-7^5 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 5^7}{7^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 5^1}$$

$$7667 := \frac{-7^1 - 6^8 + 6^{12} + 7^9}{-7^1 - 6^5 + 6^7 + 7^5}$$

$$7669 := \frac{7^7 - 6^3 - 6^7 - 9^4}{7^2 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$7672 := \frac{7^4 + 6^7 + 7^5 + 2^6}{7^0 + 6^2 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$7672 := \frac{7^4 + 6^7 + 7^5 + 2^6}{7^0 + 6^2 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$7673 := \frac{7^1 - 6^4 + 7^4 + 3^8}{-7^0 + 6^1 - 7^0 - 3^1}$$

$$7674 := \frac{7^5 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 4^8}{7^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 4^2}$$

$$7674 := \frac{7^5 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 4^8}{7^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 4^2}$$

$$7675 := \frac{7^7 - 6^7 - 7^9 + 5^{11}}{-7^0 - 6^1 + 7^5 - 5^6}$$

$$7676 := \frac{-7^5 + 6^1 - 7^9 + 6^{10}}{7^1 - 6^1 + 7^4 + 6^3}$$

$$7677 := \frac{-7^0 + 6^5 - 7^2 - 7^2}{-7^0 - 6^1 + 7^0 + 7^1}$$

$$7678 := \frac{7^7 - 6^9 - 7^8 + 8^8}{7^1 + 6^3 + 7^1 - 8^0}$$

$$7679 := \frac{-7^2 + 6^5 - 7^2 + 9^0}{-7^0 - 6^1 - 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7682 := \frac{7^0 + 6^0 - 8^3 + 2^{13}}{-7^0 - 6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$7683 := \frac{7^3 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 3^{10}}{7^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^2}$$

$$7683 := \frac{7^3 + 6^2 + 8^5 + 3^{10}}{7^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^2}$$

$$7684 := \frac{-7^5 + 6^6 - 8^0 + 4^9}{-7^0 + 6^2 - 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7685 := \frac{7^6 - 6^5 - 8^5 - 5^6}{7^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 5^1}$$

$$7687 := \frac{-7^2 + 6^4 + 8^4 + 7^6}{7^0 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$7688 := \frac{7^7 + 6^7 + 8^0 - 8^4}{-7^0 + 6^3 - 8^1 - 8^2}$$

$$7689 := \frac{7^5 + 6^6 + 8^3 + 9^5}{7^0 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 9^0}$$

$$7689 := \frac{7^5 + 6^6 + 8^3 + 9^5}{7^0 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 9^0}$$

$$7692 := \frac{7^4 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 2^1}{7^0 + 6^1 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$7692 := \frac{7^4 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 2^1}{7^0 + 6^1 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$7693 := \frac{-7^0 + 6^5 - 9^0 - 3^4}{-7^0 + 6^1 - 9^0 - 3^1}$$

$$7694 := \frac{7^6 - 6^4 + 9^2 - 4^5}{7^0 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 4^1}$$

$$7695 := \frac{-7^0 + 6^5 - 9^2 + 5^0}{7^0 - 6^1 + 9^0 + 5^1}$$

$$7696 := \frac{7^1 - 6^1 - 9^2 + 6^5}{-7^0 - 6^0 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$7697 := \frac{7^0 + 6^5 - 9^2 + 7^0}{-7^0 - 6^1 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$7698 := \frac{7^3 + 6^3 + 9^5 + 8^5}{7^0 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 8^0}$$

$$7698 := \frac{7^3 + 6^3 + 9^5 + 8^5}{7^0 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 8^0}$$

$$7699 := \frac{7^1 - 6^3 - 9^0 + 9^6}{-7^1 - 6^1 + 9^0 + 9^2}$$

$$7704 := \frac{7^5 + 7^8 + 0^1 + 4^6}{7^3 + 7^3 + 0^0 + 4^3}$$

$$7704 := \frac{7^5 + 7^8 + 0^1 + 4^6}{7^3 + 7^3 + 0^0 + 4^3}$$

$$7720 := \frac{-7^3 + 7^5 - 2^{10} + 0^1}{-7^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 0^0}$$

$$7721 := \frac{7^2 + 7^6 - 2^{15} + 1^0}{7^0 + 7^0 + 2^3 + 1^0}$$

$$7722 := \frac{7^4 + 7^7 + 2^9 + 2^{17}}{7^1 + 7^2 + 2^2 + 2^6}$$

$$7722 := \frac{7^4 + 7^7 + 2^9 + 2^{17}}{7^1 + 7^2 + 2^2 + 2^6}$$

$$7723 := \frac{7^4 + 7^8 + 2^{15} + 3^1}{7^1 + 7^1 + 2^3 + 3^6}$$

$$7723 := \frac{7^4 + 7^8 + 2^{15} + 3^1}{7^1 + 7^1 + 2^3 + 3^6}$$

$$7724 := \frac{7^0 + 7^3 + 2^7 + 4^9}{7^0 + 7^0 + 2^4 + 4^2}$$

$$7724 := \frac{7^0 + 7^3 + 2^7 + 4^9}{7^0 + 7^0 + 2^4 + 4^2}$$

$$7725 := \frac{7^4 + 7^4 + 2^{11} + 5^7}{7^0 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$7725 := \frac{7^4 + 7^4 + 2^{11} + 5^7}{7^0 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$7726 := \frac{7^0 - 7^2 - 2^1 + 6^5}{-7^0 - 7^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$7726 := \frac{7^0 - 7^2 - 2^1 + 6^5}{-7^0 - 7^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$7727 := \frac{-7^2 + 7^4 - 2^{12} + 7^6}{-7^0 + 7^0 + 2^3 + 7^1}$$

$$7728 := \frac{-7^0 + 7^2 + 2^{13} - 8^3}{-7^0 - 7^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$7729 := \frac{7^0 + 7^1 + 2^{15} + 9^6}{7^0 + 7^1 + 2^6 + 9^0}$$

$$7729 := \frac{7^0 + 7^1 + 2^{15} + 9^6}{7^0 + 7^1 + 2^6 + 9^0}$$

$$7731 := \frac{7^0 + 7^{10} + 3^3 + 1^0}{7^2 + 7^5 + 3^9 - 1^0}$$

$$7732 := \frac{-7^0 - 7^9 + 3^{17} + 2^0}{-7^0 - 7^1 + 3^9 - 2^{13}}$$

$$7733 := \frac{7^6 + 7^6 + 3^8 + 3^{12}}{7^2 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$7733 := \frac{7^6 + 7^6 + 3^8 + 3^{12}}{7^2 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$7735 := \frac{7^2 + 7^6 + 3^7 + 5^8}{7^1 + 7^1 + 3^3 + 5^2}$$

$$7735 := \frac{7^2 + 7^6 + 3^7 + 5^8}{7^1 + 7^1 + 3^3 + 5^2}$$

$$7736 := \frac{-7^0 + 7^7 + 3^9 - 6^0}{-7^0 - 7^1 + 3^4 + 6^2}$$

$$7737 := \frac{7^3 + 7^5 + 3^{12} + 7^8}{7^2 + 7^3 + 3^4 + 7^3}$$

$$7737 := \frac{7^3 + 7^5 + 3^{12} + 7^8}{7^2 + 7^3 + 3^4 + 7^3}$$

$$7738 := \frac{7^1 + 7^8 + 3^0 + 8^0}{7^0 + 7^1 + 3^6 + 8^1}$$

$$7738 := \frac{7^1 + 7^8 + 3^0 + 8^0}{7^0 + 7^1 + 3^6 + 8^1}$$

$$7739 := \frac{7^3 + 7^6 - 3^6 + 9^4}{7^1 + 7^1 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$7742 := \frac{-7^1 + 7^7 + 4^9 - 2^{15}}{7^0 + 7^1 + 4^3 + 2^6}$$

$$7743 := \frac{-7^4 + 7^6 + 4^7 - 3^0}{-7^0 + 7^0 + 4^2 + 3^0}$$

$$7744 := \frac{-7^4 + 7^6 + 4^2 + 4^7}{-7^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 4^2}$$

$$7746 := \frac{-7^1 - 7^1 - 4^2 + 6^5}{-7^0 - 7^0 + 4^1 - 6^0}$$

$$7748 := \frac{7^6 + 7^7 + 4^8 + 8^3}{7^0 + 7^0 + 4^3 + 8^2}$$

$$7748 := \frac{7^6 + 7^7 + 4^8 + 8^3}{7^0 + 7^0 + 4^3 + 8^2}$$

$$7749 := \frac{-7^4 - 7^4 - 4^1 + 9^5}{7^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$7753 := \frac{-7^4 - 7^4 + 5^4 + 3^9}{-7^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$7755 := \frac{7^0 + 7^2 - 5^4 + 5^7}{7^0 + 7^1 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7756 := \frac{-7^5 + 7^7 - 5^6 + 6^0}{7^2 + 7^2 + 5^1 - 6^0}$$

$$7757 := \frac{-7^1 - 7^5 - 5^0 + 7^7}{7^0 + 7^2 + 5^1 + 7^2}$$

$$7759 := \frac{-7^2 - 7^2 + 5^6 - 9^1}{-7^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$7785 := \frac{7^3 + 7^{10} + 8^1 + 5^5}{7^2 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 5^5}$$

$$7822 := \frac{7^6 + 8^0 - 2^6 - 2^8}{7^0 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 2^2}$$

$$7761 := \frac{-7^1 - 7^1 + 6^5 - 1^0}{7^0 - 7^1 + 6^1 + 1^0}$$

$$7786 := \frac{7^0 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 6^5}{7^0 - 7^1 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$7823 := \frac{7^1 + 8^3 + 2^2 + 3^{12}}{7^0 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 3^3}$$

$$7762 := \frac{7^0 + 7^0 + 6^5 - 2^4}{-7^0 - 7^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$7786 := \frac{7^0 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 6^5}{7^0 - 7^1 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$7823 := \frac{7^1 + 8^3 + 2^2 + 3^{12}}{7^0 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 3^3}$$

$$7763 := \frac{7^4 + 7^6 + 6^0 + 3^9}{7^0 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 3^2}$$

$$7789 := \frac{7^1 + 7^5 - 8^1 + 9^4}{7^0 + 7^0 - 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$7824 := \frac{7^6 - 8^0 - 2^5 - 4^4}{7^0 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$7763 := \frac{7^4 + 7^6 + 6^0 + 3^9}{7^0 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 3^2}$$

$$7790 := \frac{7^0 + 7^5 + 9^4 + 0^0}{7^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 0^1}$$

$$7825 := \frac{7^2 + 8^2 + 2^9 + 5^8}{7^0 + 8^1 + 2^4 + 5^2}$$

$$7764 := \frac{7^6 + 7^7 + 6^8 + 4^8}{7^0 + 7^3 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$7790 := \frac{7^0 + 7^5 + 9^4 + 0^0}{7^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 0^1}$$

$$7825 := \frac{7^2 + 8^2 + 2^9 + 5^8}{7^0 + 8^1 + 2^4 + 5^2}$$

$$7764 := \frac{7^6 + 7^7 + 6^8 + 4^8}{7^0 + 7^3 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$7792 := \frac{7^1 + 7^5 + 9^4 + 2^0}{-7^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$7826 := \frac{7^2 - 8^0 + 2^1 + 6^5}{-7^0 - 8^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$7765 := \frac{7^0 - 7^1 + 6^5 - 5^1}{7^0 + 7^0 - 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$7793 := \frac{-7^6 - 7^6 - 9^1 + 3^{12}}{7^0 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 3^3}$$

$$7827 := \frac{-7^1 - 8^3 + 2^{16} - 7^4}{-7^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 7^1}$$

$$7766 := \frac{-7^0 - 7^2 - 6^5 + 6^6}{-7^0 - 7^0 + 6^0 + 6^1}$$

$$7795 := \frac{7^3 - 7^5 - 9^0 + 5^8}{7^1 + 7^1 + 9^1 + 5^2}$$

$$7828 := \frac{-7^4 + 8^0 + 2^{16} - 8^3}{-7^0 - 8^0 + 2^1 + 8^1}$$

$$7767 := \frac{-7^0 - 7^0 + 6^5 - 7^1}{-7^0 + 7^0 - 6^1 + 7^1}$$

$$7798 := \frac{7^2 + 7^6 - 9^3 + 8^0}{-7^0 - 7^0 + 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$7829 := \frac{-7^0 - 8^3 + 2^{12} + 9^5}{-7^0 - 8^0 + 2^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7768 := \frac{-7^0 + 7^0 + 6^5 - 8^1}{-7^0 - 7^1 + 6^0 + 8^1}$$

$$7802 := \frac{7^0 + 8^5 + 0^0 + 2^{17}}{7^1 - 8^0 - 0^0 + 2^4}$$

$$7831 := \frac{7^5 + 8^6 - 3^{11} - 1^0}{7^0 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 1^0}$$

$$7769 := \frac{7^0 + 7^0 + 6^5 - 9^1}{-7^0 - 7^0 - 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$7805 := \frac{-7^1 - 8^1 + 0^1 + 5^6}{-7^0 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7832 := \frac{7^5 + 8^5 + 3^{10} + 2^{10}}{7^0 + 8^1 + 3^0 + 2^2}$$

$$7773 := \frac{7^2 + 7^3 + 7^7 + 3^1}{7^1 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 3^0}$$

$$7808 := \frac{7^7 + 8^1 + 0^0 + 8^4}{7^2 - 8^1 + 0^0 + 8^2}$$

$$7832 := \frac{7^5 + 8^5 + 3^{10} + 2^{10}}{7^0 + 8^1 + 3^0 + 2^2}$$

$$7773 := \frac{7^2 + 7^3 + 7^7 + 3^1}{7^1 + 7^2 + 7^2 + 3^0}$$

$$7809 := \frac{7^6 - 8^3 - 0^0 - 9^0}{-7^0 + 8^1 - 0^0 + 9^1}$$

$$7833 := \frac{7^6 + 8^1 - 3^4 - 3^4}{7^0 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 3^1}$$

$$7782 := \frac{-7^3 + 7^6 - 8^2 - 2^9}{-7^0 - 7^0 + 8^0 + 2^4}$$

$$7815 := \frac{7^1 - 8^0 - 1^0 + 5^6}{-7^0 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7834 := \frac{7^8 + 8^2 + 3^5 + 4^7}{7^1 + 8^0 + 3^6 + 4^0}$$

$$7783 := \frac{7^3 - 7^6 - 8^5 + 3^{12}}{7^1 + 7^1 + 8^1 + 3^3}$$

$$7816 := \frac{7^2 - 8^1 - 1^0 + 6^5}{-7^1 + 8^0 + 1^0 + 6^1}$$

$$7834 := \frac{7^8 + 8^2 + 3^5 + 4^7}{7^1 + 8^0 + 3^6 + 4^0}$$

$$7784 := \frac{-7^4 - 7^5 - 8^5 + 4^9}{-7^1 + 7^2 + 8^0 - 4^2}$$

$$7820 := \frac{-7^6 + 8^0 + 2^{19} + 0^1}{7^2 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 0^0}$$

$$7835 := \frac{7^2 - 8^0 - 3^1 + 5^6}{-7^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7785 := \frac{7^3 + 7^{10} + 8^1 + 5^5}{7^2 + 7^3 + 8^5 + 5^5}$$

$$7821 := \frac{-7^2 - 8^3 + 2^{20} - 1^0}{-7^0 + 8^1 + 2^7 - 1^0}$$

$$7836 := \frac{7^3 + 8^1 + 3^2 + 6^6}{7^0 + 8^0 + 3^1 + 6^0}$$

$$7837 := \frac{-7^4 - 8^1 - 3^8 + 7^5}{7^0 - 8^1 + 3^0 + 7^1}$$

$$7838 := \frac{7^6 + 8^1 - 3^{10} + 8^4}{-7^0 - 8^0 + 3^2 + 8^0}$$

$$7839 := \frac{7^6 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 9^5}{7^1 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$7839 := \frac{7^6 + 8^5 + 3^7 + 9^5}{7^1 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$7840 := \frac{7^6 - 8^2 + 4^2 - 0^0}{-7^0 - 8^0 + 4^2 + 0^0}$$

$$7842 := \frac{-7^3 - 8^1 + 4^0 + 2^{13}}{-7^0 - 8^0 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$7843 := \frac{7^5 + 8^2 + 4^7 + 3^{12}}{7^0 + 8^2 + 4^1 + 3^1}$$

$$7843 := \frac{7^5 + 8^2 + 4^7 + 3^{12}}{7^0 + 8^2 + 4^1 + 3^1}$$

$$7844 := \frac{7^6 - 8^0 - 4^1 + 4^2}{-7^0 - 8^0 + 4^0 + 4^2}$$

$$7845 := \frac{-7^1 + 8^1 + 4^3 + 5^6}{-7^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7846 := \frac{7^6 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 6^2}{7^1 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$7846 := \frac{7^6 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 6^2}{7^1 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$7847 := \frac{-7^1 - 8^0 + 4^3 + 7^6}{-7^0 - 8^0 + 4^2 + 7^0}$$

$$7848 := \frac{-7^3 - 8^0 + 4^6 + 8^4}{-7^0 - 8^0 + 4^1 - 8^0}$$

$$7849 := \frac{7^6 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 9^2}{7^0 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 9^1}$$

$$7849 := \frac{7^6 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 9^2}{7^0 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 9^1}$$

$$7851 := \frac{7^6 - 8^1 + 5^3 - 1^0}{7^0 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 1^0}$$

$$7852 := \frac{7^3 + 8^9 + 5^6 + 2^{12}}{7^5 + 8^1 + 5^2 + 2^8}$$

$$7852 := \frac{7^3 + 8^9 + 5^6 + 2^{12}}{7^5 + 8^1 + 5^2 + 2^8}$$

$$7853 := \frac{7^6 + 8^2 + 5^0 + 3^4}{7^0 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 3^0}$$

$$7853 := \frac{7^6 + 8^2 + 5^0 + 3^4}{7^0 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 3^0}$$

$$7854 := \frac{7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3}{7^1 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$7854 := \frac{7^3 + 8^1 + 5^7 + 4^3}{7^1 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$7855 := \frac{7^2 + 8^7 - 5^0 - 5^6}{7^1 + 8^1 + 5^3 + 5^3}$$

$$7856 := \frac{-7^0 + 8^1 + 5^6 - 6^5}{-7^0 + 8^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$7857 := \frac{-7^3 + 8^5 - 5^7 + 7^7}{-7^1 - 8^3 + 5^4 - 7^1}$$

$$7858 := \frac{7^4 + 8^4 + 5^2 + 8^5}{-7^0 - 8^0 - 5^0 + 8^1}$$

$$7859 := \frac{7^2 + 8^6 + 5^3 + 9^6}{7^1 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 9^2}$$

$$7859 := \frac{7^2 + 8^6 + 5^3 + 9^6}{7^1 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 9^2}$$

$$7860 := \frac{-7^1 + 8^3 + 6^6 - 0^0}{-7^0 + 8^0 + 6^1 + 0^1}$$

$$7861 := \frac{-7^0 + 8^3 + 6^6 - 1^0}{7^1 - 8^0 - 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$7862 := \frac{7^6 + 8^0 + 6^3 + 2^6}{7^1 + 8^0 + 6^1 + 2^0}$$

$$7862 := \frac{7^6 + 8^0 + 6^3 + 2^6}{7^1 + 8^0 + 6^1 + 2^0}$$

$$7863 := \frac{7^0 + 8^3 + 6^6 + 3^2}{7^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$$

$$7863 := \frac{7^0 + 8^3 + 6^6 + 3^2}{7^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$$

$$7864 := \frac{7^3 + 8^0 + 6^5 - 4^4}{-7^0 - 8^0 - 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7865 := \frac{7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7}{7^1 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7865 := \frac{7^1 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 5^7}{7^1 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7866 := \frac{-7^1 + 8^5 - 6^0 - 6^4}{7^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$7867 := \frac{7^3 - 8^6 + 6^7 - 7^4}{-7^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 7^0}$$

$$7868 := \frac{-7^0 + 8^0 - 6^4 + 8^5}{7^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$7869 := \frac{7^2 + 8^8 + 6^6 + 9^0}{7^2 + 8^2 + 6^4 + 9^3}$$

$$7869 := \frac{7^2 + 8^8 + 6^6 + 9^0}{7^2 + 8^2 + 6^4 + 9^3}$$

$$7871 := \frac{-7^0 + 8^6 - 7^4 + 1^0}{-7^1 - 8^1 + 7^2 - 1^0}$$

$$7872 := \frac{7^3 + 8^1 + 7^4 + 2^{17}}{7^0 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 2^3}$$

$$7872 := \frac{7^3 + 8^1 + 7^4 + 2^{17}}{7^0 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 2^3}$$

$$7873 := \frac{7^4 - 8^1 + 7^7 + 3^6}{7^1 + 8^2 + 7^1 + 3^3}$$

$$7874 := \frac{7^4 + 8^4 + 7^4 - 4^5}{-7^0 - 8^0 - 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7875 := \frac{7^3 + 8^1 + 7^6 + 5^3}{7^0 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 5^1}$$

$$7875 := \frac{7^3 + 8^1 + 7^6 + 5^3}{7^0 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 5^1}$$

$$7876 := \frac{7^2 + 8^5 + 7^7 + 6^{10}}{7^0 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 6^5}$$

$$7876 := \frac{7^2 + 8^5 + 7^7 + 6^{10}}{7^0 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 6^5}$$

$$7877 := \frac{7^0 + 8^3 - 7^1 + 7^6}{-7^0 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 7^1}$$

$$7878 := \frac{7^0 + 8^1 + 7^6 + 8^3}{-7^0 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 8^1}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 7879 := \frac{7^5 - 8^3 + 7^6 - 9^0}{7^0 + 8^1 + 7^1 + 9^0} & 7920 := \frac{7^7 + 9^1 + 2^7 + 0^1}{7^1 + 9^2 + 2^4 + 0^1} & 7929 := \frac{7^7 + 9^2 + 2^{13} + 9^3}{7^1 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 9^2} \\
 7882 := \frac{7^7 - 8^0 - 8^1 + 2^{19}}{-7^3 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 2^9} & 7920 := \frac{7^7 + 9^1 + 2^7 + 0^1}{7^1 + 9^2 + 2^4 + 0^1} & 7930 := \frac{-7^2 - 9^2 + 3^{12} - 0^0}{7^2 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 0^1} \\
 7883 := \frac{7^2 - 8^0 - 8^6 + 3^{13}}{-7^2 + 8^0 - 8^3 + 3^6} & 7921 := \frac{7^6 + 9^2 + 2^{15} + 1^0}{7^1 + 9^1 + 2^1 + 1^1} & 7932 := \frac{7^0 + 9^0 + 3^{12} + 2^0}{7^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 2^6} \\
 7884 := \frac{-7^4 + 8^0 - 8^2 + 4^8}{-7^0 + 8^0 - 8^1 + 4^2} & 7921 := \frac{7^6 + 9^2 + 2^{15} + 1^0}{7^1 + 9^1 + 2^1 + 1^1} & 7932 := \frac{7^0 + 9^0 + 3^{12} + 2^0}{7^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 2^6} \\
 7889 := \frac{-7^1 + 8^0 + 8^7 - 9^4}{7^2 - 8^0 - 8^3 + 9^3} & 7922 := \frac{7^5 + 9^4 + 2^7 + 2^{13}}{7^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 2^0} & 7933 := \frac{7^6 + 9^0 - 3^3 - 3^8}{7^0 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 3^2} \\
 7892 := \frac{7^5 + 8^1 + 9^4 + 2^{13}}{7^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 2^0} & 7922 := \frac{7^5 + 9^4 + 2^7 + 2^{13}}{7^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 2^0} & 7935 := \frac{7^0 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 5^6}{-7^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 5^0} \\
 7892 := \frac{7^5 + 8^1 + 9^4 + 2^{13}}{7^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 2^0} & 7923 := \frac{7^2 + 9^3 + 2^{17} + 3^{11}}{7^0 + 9^1 + 2^1 + 3^3} & 7937 := \frac{7^5 + 9^3 + 3^5 + 7^7}{-7^0 + 9^2 + 3^3 - 7^0} \\
 7893 := \frac{-7^3 - 8^3 + 9^4 + 3^7}{-7^0 - 8^1 + 9^0 + 3^2} & 7923 := \frac{7^2 + 9^3 + 2^{17} + 3^{11}}{7^0 + 9^1 + 2^1 + 3^3} & 7939 := \frac{7^3 - 9^0 + 3^{15} - 9^5}{7^3 - 9^0 + 3^6 + 9^3} \\
 7894 := \frac{7^7 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 4^5}{7^1 + 8^1 + 9^2 + 4^2} & 7924 := \frac{7^5 + 9^6 + 2^{17} + 4^8}{7^0 + 9^2 + 2^3 + 4^1} & 7942 := \frac{7^7 + 9^4 + 4^{14} + 2^3}{7^3 + 9^3 + 4^3 + 2^{15}} \\
 7894 := \frac{7^7 + 8^3 + 9^5 + 4^5}{7^1 + 8^1 + 9^2 + 4^2} & 7924 := \frac{7^5 + 9^6 + 2^{17} + 4^8}{7^0 + 9^2 + 2^3 + 4^1} & 7942 := \frac{7^7 + 9^4 + 4^{14} + 2^3}{7^3 + 9^3 + 4^3 + 2^{15}} \\
 7895 := \frac{7^7 + 8^1 - 9^6 + 5^1}{7^0 - 8^1 - 9^2 + 5^3} & 7925 := \frac{7^0 + 9^4 + 2^{19} + 5^3}{7^0 + 9^0 + 2^6 + 5^0} & 7943 := \frac{7^1 + 9^3 + 4^1 + 3^{12}}{7^0 + 9^0 + 4^3 + 3^0} \\
 7896 := \frac{-7^0 - 8^1 + 9^3 + 6^6}{-7^0 - 8^0 + 9^1 - 6^0} & 7925 := \frac{7^0 + 9^4 + 2^{19} + 5^3}{7^0 + 9^0 + 2^6 + 5^0} & 7943 := \frac{7^1 + 9^3 + 4^1 + 3^{12}}{7^0 + 9^0 + 4^3 + 3^0} \\
 7897 := \frac{-7^5 + 8^6 + 9^4 - 7^6}{7^0 + 8^1 + 9^0 + 7^1} & 7926 := \frac{7^6 + 9^0 + 2^{10} + 6^3}{7^0 + 9^1 + 2^2 + 6^0} & 7944 := \frac{7^1 + 9^1 + 4^9 + 4^9}{7^2 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 4^1} \\
 7902 := \frac{-7^4 + 9^2 + 0^1 + 2^{16}}{-7^0 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 2^3} & 7926 := \frac{7^6 + 9^0 + 2^{10} + 6^3}{7^0 + 9^1 + 2^2 + 6^0} & 7945 := \frac{7^1 + 9^1 + 4^9 + 5^2}{7^1 + 9^1 + 4^2 + 5^0} \\
 7904 := \frac{-7^7 - 9^5 + 0^1 + 4^{10}}{7^1 + 9^1 + 0^0 + 4^1} & 7927 := \frac{7^6 + 9^0 + 2^{16} + 7^7}{7^1 + 9^2 + 2^5 + 7^1} & 7945 := \frac{7^1 + 9^1 + 4^9 + 5^2}{7^1 + 9^1 + 4^2 + 5^0} \\
 7905 := \frac{7^6 + 9^0 + 0^1 - 5^7}{-7^0 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 5^1} & 7927 := \frac{7^6 + 9^0 + 2^{16} + 7^7}{7^1 + 9^2 + 2^5 + 7^1} & 7946 := \frac{7^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 6^6}{7^0 + 9^0 + 4^1 + 6^0} \\
 7906 := \frac{7^2 + 9^2 + 0^1 + 6^5}{-7^0 + 9^0 + 0^1 + 6^0} & 7928 := \frac{7^3 + 9^4 + 2^9 + 8^3}{-7^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 8^0} & 7946 := \frac{7^4 + 9^4 + 4^1 + 6^6}{7^0 + 9^0 + 4^1 + 6^0} \\
 7913 := \frac{-7^0 - 9^0 - 1^0 + 3^{17}}{7^5 - 9^3 - 1^0 + 3^5} & 7929 := \frac{7^7 + 9^2 + 2^{13} + 9^3}{7^1 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 9^2} & 7947 := \frac{7^2 + 9^1 + 4^9 + 7^2}{7^0 + 9^1 + 4^2 + 7^1}
 \end{array}$$

$$7947 := \frac{7^2 + 9^1 + 4^9 + 7^2}{7^0 + 9^1 + 4^2 + 7^1}$$

$$7948 := \frac{-7^3 - 9^2 + 4^7 - 8^2}{-7^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$7949 := \frac{7^8 - 9^1 - 4^6 - 9^7}{7^2 + 9^0 + 4^3 + 9^1}$$

$$7953 := \frac{7^6 - 9^4 - 5^6 - 3^3}{7^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$7955 := \frac{-7^0 - 9^1 + 5^5 + 5^{10}}{-7^0 + 9^3 - 5^3 + 5^4}$$

$$7957 := \frac{7^5 + 9^2 + 5^8 + 7^6}{7^1 + 9^1 + 5^0 + 7^2}$$

$$7957 := \frac{7^5 + 9^2 + 5^8 + 7^6}{7^1 + 9^1 + 5^0 + 7^2}$$

$$7958 := \frac{-7^6 + 9^6 + 5^2 - 8^0}{7^2 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$7959 := \frac{7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3}{7^1 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$7959 := \frac{7^1 + 9^3 + 5^7 + 9^3}{7^1 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$7961 := \frac{7^5 - 9^3 + 6^8 - 1^0}{-7^0 - 9^0 + 6^3 - 1^0}$$

$$7962 := \frac{7^4 + 9^0 + 6^1 + 2^{20}}{7^1 + 9^2 + 6^2 + 2^3}$$

$$7963 := \frac{7^7 + 9^2 + 6^9 + 3^3}{7^3 + 9^2 + 6^3 + 3^6}$$

$$7963 := \frac{7^7 + 9^2 + 6^9 + 3^3}{7^3 + 9^2 + 6^3 + 3^6}$$

$$7964 := \frac{7^3 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 4^5}{-7^0 - 9^0 - 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$7965 := \frac{-7^3 + 9^1 - 6^1 + 5^8}{7^1 + 9^0 + 6^2 + 5^1}$$

$$7966 := \frac{-7^2 - 9^4 - 6^3 + 6^6}{-7^0 - 9^0 + 6^0 + 6^1}$$

$$7967 := \frac{-7^4 + 9^5 - 6^1 - 7^5}{-7^0 - 9^0 + 6^1 + 7^0}$$

$$7968 := \frac{7^4 + 9^6 + 6^1 + 8^1}{7^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 8^2}$$

$$7968 := \frac{7^4 + 9^6 + 6^1 + 8^1}{7^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 8^2}$$

$$7969 := \frac{7^6 - 9^0 - 6^6 + 9^3}{7^0 + 9^0 + 6^1 + 9^0}$$

$$7973 := \frac{7^0 - 9^4 + 7^7 - 3^9}{7^2 + 9^0 + 7^2 + 3^0}$$

$$7975 := \frac{7^4 + 9^2 - 7^5 + 5^7}{7^0 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 5^1}$$

$$7978 := \frac{-7^6 + 9^7 + 7^7 + 8^0}{7^3 + 9^0 + 7^3 + 8^0}$$

$$7980 := \frac{-7^5 - 9^0 + 8^5 + 0^1}{-7^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 0^0}$$

$$7982 := \frac{7^6 + 9^3 + 8^3 + 2^{15}}{7^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 2^4}$$

$$7982 := \frac{7^6 + 9^3 + 8^3 + 2^{15}}{7^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 2^4}$$

$$7983 := \frac{7^3 + 9^4 + 8^5 + 3^5}{-7^0 - 9^0 + 8^1 - 3^0}$$

$$7984 := \frac{7^3 + 9^3 + 8^6 + 4^4}{7^1 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 4^2}$$

$$7984 := \frac{7^3 + 9^3 + 8^6 + 4^4}{7^1 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 4^2}$$

$$7985 := \frac{7^3 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 5^6}{-7^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 5^0}$$

$$7986 := \frac{7^3 + 9^7 + 8^3 + 6^5}{7^0 + 9^2 + 8^3 + 6^1}$$

$$7986 := \frac{7^3 + 9^7 + 8^3 + 6^5}{7^0 + 9^2 + 8^3 + 6^1}$$

$$7987 := \frac{-7^4 - 9^0 + 8^7 + 7^6}{-7^0 - 9^0 - 8^2 + 7^3}$$

$$7988 := \frac{7^8 - 9^0 - 8^5 + 8^9}{7^5 + 9^3 - 8^1 - 8^1}$$

$$7989 := \frac{-7^9 - 9^1 - 8^5 + 9^8}{7^3 - 9^0 - 8^1 - 9^0}$$

$$7994 := \frac{7^7 - 9^2 - 9^2 + 4^0}{7^1 - 9^0 + 9^2 + 4^2}$$

$$7995 := \frac{-7^3 + 9^3 + 9^7 - 5^9}{7^3 + 9^0 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$7997 := \frac{7^2 + 9^0 + 9^7 - 7^5}{7^3 - 9^1 - 9^2 + 7^3}$$

$$7998 := \frac{7^5 - 9^2 - 9^3 - 8^0}{-7^0 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$7999 := \frac{7^5 + 9^0 - 9^2 - 9^3}{-7^0 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8023 := \frac{-8^3 - 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^{11}}{8^1 + 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^2}$$

$$8025 := \frac{-8^2 + 0^0 + 2^{19} + 5^8}{8^0 + 0^1 - 2^9 + 5^4}$$

$$8027 := \frac{-8^1 - 0^0 + 2^{18} - 7^6}{8^0 + 0^1 + 2^4 + 7^0}$$

$$8029 := \frac{8^6 - 0^0 - 2^5 + 9^5}{-8^0 + 0^1 + 2^5 + 9^1}$$

$$8032 := \frac{8^1 - 0^0 + 3^{14} + 2^{12}}{8^3 + 0^0 + 3^4 + 2^1}$$

$$8033 := \frac{8^6 + 0^0 - 3^8 - 3^8}{8^0 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 3^3}$$

$$8035 := \frac{8^5 + 0^1 - 3^1 - 5^4}{8^0 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8036 := \frac{-8^2 - 0^0 - 3^3 + 6^8}{8^0 + 0^0 - 3^2 + 6^3}$$

$$8039 := \frac{8^5 - 0^0 + 3^8 + 9^6}{-8^0 + 0^1 - 3^2 + 9^2}$$

$$8047 := \frac{-8^2 - 0^0 + 4^{10} - 7^4}{8^2 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 7^2}$$

$$8048 := \frac{-8^3 + 0^1 - 4^3 + 8^5}{8^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8052 := \frac{8^3 - 0^0 + 5^6 - 2^5}{-8^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8053 := \frac{8^3 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 3^{14}}{8^3 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 3^4}$$

$$8053 := \frac{8^3 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 3^{14}}{8^3 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 3^4}$$

$$8054 := \frac{8^3 + 0^0 + 5^5 + 4^9}{8^1 - 0^0 + 5^2 + 4^0}$$

$$8055 := \frac{8^4 - 0^0 - 5^2 + 5^8}{-8^0 + 0^1 + 5^2 + 5^2}$$

$$8056 := \frac{8^5 - 0^0 + 5^{12} + 6^8}{-8^3 - 0^0 - 5^6 + 6^6}$$

$$8058 := \frac{-8^3 + 0^0 - 5^2 + 8^5}{8^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8059 := \frac{-8^4 + 0^1 + 5^7 + 9^4}{8^1 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8062 := \frac{8^2 + 0^1 + 6^9 - 2^{14}}{8^1 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 2^{10}}$$

$$8064 := \frac{-8^4 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 4^9}{-8^0 + 0^0 + 6^2 - 4^1}$$

$$8065 := \frac{8^3 - 0^0 - 6^1 + 5^6}{-8^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8066 := \frac{8^7 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 6^1}{8^1 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 6^3}$$

$$8066 := \frac{8^7 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 6^1}{8^1 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 6^3}$$

$$8067 := \frac{8^1 + 0^1 + 6^7 + 7^4}{-8^0 - 0^0 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$8072 := \frac{8^5 + 0^0 - 7^4 + 2^{17}}{8^1 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 2^2}$$

$$8073 := \frac{-8^4 + 0^1 + 7^3 + 3^{14}}{8^3 + 0^1 - 7^0 + 3^4}$$

$$8075 := \frac{8^5 + 0^1 - 7^3 - 5^3}{8^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8076 := \frac{-8^1 + 0^0 + 7^7 + 6^3}{8^2 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 6^2}$$

$$8079 := \frac{8^6 + 0^0 + 7^6 - 9^2}{-8^0 + 0^1 + 7^2 - 9^0}$$

$$8092 := \frac{8^4 + 0^0 - 9^5 + 2^{19}}{-8^1 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^6}$$

$$8093 := \frac{-8^1 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 3^{14}}{8^3 - 0^0 - 9^0 + 3^4}$$

$$8096 := \frac{8^5 + 0^0 - 9^4 + 6^6}{8^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 6^1}$$

$$8097 := \frac{8^1 - 0^0 + 9^7 - 7^7}{8^2 + 0^0 + 9^2 + 7^3}$$

$$8113 := \frac{-8^4 - 1^0 + 1^0 + 3^{12}}{8^2 - 1^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8123 := \frac{8^5 - 1^0 - 2^5 - 3^5}{8^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8123 := \frac{8^5 - 1^5 - 2^5 - 3^5}{8^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8125 := \frac{-8^1 - 1^0 + 2^{14} - 5^3}{-8^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8126 := \frac{-8^2 - 1^0 + 2^{13} - 6^0}{-8^0 - 1^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$8127 := \frac{-8^3 - 1^0 + 2^{16} - 7^1}{-8^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 7^1}$$

$$8128 := \frac{-8^0 + 1^0 + 2^{13} - 8^2}{-8^0 - 1^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$8129 := \frac{-8^3 - 1^0 + 2^{16} + 9^1}{-8^0 - 1^0 + 2^0 + 9^1}$$

$$8132 := \frac{-8^2 + 1^0 + 3^1 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 1^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8134 := \frac{8^6 - 1^0 - 3^{10} + 4^4}{-8^0 + 1^0 + 3^2 + 4^2}$$

$$8135 := \frac{8^4 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 5^4}{8^1 - 1^0 + 3^0 - 5^1}$$

$$8136 := \frac{8^5 + 1^0 - 3^2 - 6^3}{8^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8137 := \frac{8^7 + 1^0 + 3^{12} - 7^3}{8^1 - 1^0 - 3^3 + 7^3}$$

$$8138 := \frac{8^3 + 1^0 - 3^6 + 8^5}{8^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8143 := \frac{8^9 - 1^0 + 4^{13} + 3^{15}}{8^5 + 1^0 - 4^6 - 3^7}$$

$$8145 := \frac{8^5 + 1^0 - 4^3 - 5^3}{8^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8146 := \frac{8^0 + 1^0 + 4^8 + 6^5}{8^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$8146 := \frac{8^0 + 1^0 + 4^8 + 6^5}{8^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$8147 := \frac{8^3 - 1^0 - 4^5 + 7^5}{-8^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8152 := \frac{-8^2 - 1^0 + 5^2 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8153 := \frac{8^4 - 1^0 - 5^6 + 3^9}{-8^1 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$8154 := \frac{8^3 - 1^0 + 5^8 + 4^4}{8^1 - 1^0 + 5^2 + 4^2}$$

$$8162 := \frac{8^7 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 2^{17}}{-8^1 + 1^0 + 6^3 + 2^6}$$

$$8163 := \frac{8^5 + 1^0 - 6^2 - 3^4}{8^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8169 := \frac{-8^2 + 1^0 + 6^5 + 9^6}{-8^1 - 1^0 - 6^1 + 9^2}$$

$$8172 := \frac{8^1 + 1^0 - 7^2 + 2^{14}}{-8^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8173 := \frac{8^7 + 1^0 + 7^6 + 3^4}{8^1 + 1^0 + 7^3 - 3^4}$$

$$8174 := \frac{8^5 - 1^0 - 7^1 - 4^3}{8^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8177 := \frac{-8^1 - 1^0 - 7^1 + 7^8}{-8^4 - 1^0 + 7^4 + 7^4}$$

$$8178 := \frac{-8^1 + 1^0 - 7^2 + 8^5}{8^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8182 := \frac{-8^0 - 1^0 - 8^1 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8183 := \frac{-8^1 - 1^0 + 8^5 - 3^3}{8^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8184 := \frac{-8^0 + 1^0 - 8^2 + 4^8}{-8^0 + 1^0 - 8^1 + 4^2}$$

$$8190 := \frac{8^5 + 1^0 - 9^1 + 0^1}{8^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8192 := \frac{-8^1 - 1^0 + 9^1 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 1^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8194 := \frac{8^4 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 4^6}{-8^0 - 1^0 - 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$8196 := \frac{8^5 + 1^0 + 9^1 + 6^1}{8^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8196 := \frac{8^5 + 1^0 + 9^1 + 6^1}{8^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8200 := \frac{8^5 + 2^5 + 0^5 + 0^5}{8^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8200 := \frac{8^5 + 2^5 + 0^5 + 0^5}{8^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8200 := \frac{8^5 + 2^5 - 0^5 - 0^5}{8^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8201 := \frac{8^1 + 2^{13} + 0^1 + 1^0}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 1^0}$$

$$8202 := \frac{8^1 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 2^{15}}{8^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8202 := \frac{8^1 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 2^{15}}{8^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8203 := \frac{8^5 + 2^4 + 0^0 + 3^3}{8^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8203 := \frac{8^5 + 2^4 + 0^0 + 3^3}{8^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8204 := \frac{8^5 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 4^2}{8^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8204 := \frac{8^5 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 4^2}{8^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8205 := \frac{8^1 + 2^{13} + 0^1 + 5^1}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 5^0}$$

$$8206 := \frac{8^1 + 2^{17} + 0^1 + 6^3}{8^1 + 2^1 + 0^1 + 6^1}$$

$$8206 := \frac{8^1 + 2^{17} + 0^1 + 6^3}{8^1 + 2^1 + 0^1 + 6^1}$$

$$8207 := \frac{8^1 + 2^{13} + 0^1 + 7^1}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 7^0}$$

$$8208 := \frac{8^4 + 2^4 + 0^4 + 8^4}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 8^0}$$

$$8209 := \frac{8^1 + 2^{13} + 0^1 + 9^1}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 9^0}$$

$$8213 := \frac{8^5 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 3^4}{8^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8213 := \frac{8^5 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 3^4}{8^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8215 := \frac{-8^0 + 2^{13} - 1^0 + 5^2}{8^0 - 2^1 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8217 := \frac{8^5 - 2^{14} + 1^0 + 7^2}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8219 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{14} - 1^0 - 9^1}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8220 := \frac{-8^1 + 2^6 + 2^{14} + 0^1}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8222 := \frac{-8^0 - 2^0 + 2^5 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8223 := \frac{8^5 + 2^7 + 2^{13} + 3^3}{8^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$8223 := \frac{8^5 + 2^7 + 2^{13} + 3^3}{8^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$8224 := \frac{8^2 + 2^6 + 2^{14} + 4^7}{8^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8225 := \frac{8^5 + 2^8 + 2^{20} + 5^7}{8^1 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 5^3}$$

$$8225 := \frac{8^5 + 2^8 + 2^{20} + 5^7}{8^1 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 5^3}$$

$$8226 := \frac{8^5 + 2^1 + 2^7 + 6^1}{8^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8226 := \frac{8^5 + 2^1 + 2^7 + 6^1}{8^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8227 := \frac{-8^0 + 2^6 + 2^{14} + 7^1}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8228 := \frac{8^1 + 2^3 + 2^7 + 8^5}{8^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8229 := \frac{8^0 + 2^6 + 2^{14} + 9^1}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8230 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{13} - 3^3 + 0^0}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 0^1}$$

$$8231 := \frac{8^5 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 1^0}{8^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$8231 := \frac{8^5 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 1^0}{8^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$8232 := \frac{-8^0 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8233 := \frac{8^5 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 3^4}{8^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8233 := \frac{8^5 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 3^4}{8^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8234 := \frac{8^0 + 2^{11} + 3^{13} + 4^5}{8^0 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 4^3}$$

$$8234 := \frac{8^0 + 2^{11} + 3^{13} + 4^5}{8^0 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 4^3}$$

$$8235 := \frac{8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7}{8^0 + 2^0 + 3^1 + 5^1}$$

$$8235 := \frac{8^4 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 5^7}{8^0 + 2^0 + 3^1 + 5^1}$$

$$8236 := \frac{8^0 + 2^{13} + 3^9 + 6^9}{8^3 + 2^8 + 3^5 + 6^3}$$

$$8236 := \frac{8^0 + 2^{13} + 3^9 + 6^9}{8^3 + 2^8 + 3^5 + 6^3}$$

$$8237 := \frac{8^5 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 7^2}{8^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8237 := \frac{8^5 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 7^2}{8^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8238 := \frac{8^0 + 2^{14} + 3^3 + 8^2}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8239 := \frac{8^3 + 2^{20} + 3^{11} + 9^5}{8^1 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 9^2}$$

$$8239 := \frac{8^3 + 2^{20} + 3^{11} + 9^5}{8^1 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 9^2}$$

$$8240 := \frac{8^5 + 2^7 + 4^3 + 0^1}{8^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8240 := \frac{8^5 + 2^7 + 4^3 + 0^1}{8^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8241 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{13} - 4^2 + 1^0}{-8^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 - 1^0}$$

$$8242 := \frac{8^1 + 2^7 + 4^3 + 2^{15}}{8^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8242 := \frac{8^1 + 2^7 + 4^3 + 2^{15}}{8^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8243 := \frac{8^4 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 3^{12}}{8^1 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 3^2}$$

$$8243 := \frac{8^4 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 3^{12}}{8^1 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 3^2}$$

$$8244 := \frac{8^5 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 4^3}{8^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8244 := \frac{8^5 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 4^3}{8^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8245 := \frac{8^4 + 2^{18} + 4^{11} + 5^0}{8^1 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$8246 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{13} - 4^1 - 6^1}{-8^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 - 6^0}$$

$$8247 := \frac{8^3 + 2^{15} + 4^8 + 7^8}{8^3 + 2^7 + 4^3 + 7^1}$$

$$8247 := \frac{8^3 + 2^{15} + 4^8 + 7^8}{8^3 + 2^7 + 4^3 + 7^1}$$

$$8248 := \frac{-8^1 + 2^6 + 4^6 + 8^4}{-8^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 - 8^0}$$

$$8249 := \frac{-8^1 + 2^{13} - 4^2 + 9^2}{-8^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 - 9^0}$$

$$8250 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{13} - 5^1 - 0^0}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$8251 := \frac{-8^1 + 2^{14} + 5^3 + 1^0}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$8252 := \frac{8^0 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 2^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8253 := \frac{8^7 + 2^{17} + 5^1 + 3^4}{8^0 + 2^0 + 5^2 + 3^5}$$

$$8253 := \frac{8^7 + 2^{17} + 5^1 + 3^4}{8^0 + 2^0 + 5^2 + 3^5}$$

$$8254 := \frac{8^0 + 2^{12} + 5^7 + 4^{10}}{8^1 + 2^6 + 5^0 + 4^3}$$

$$8254 := \frac{8^0 + 2^{12} + 5^7 + 4^{10}}{8^1 + 2^6 + 5^0 + 4^3}$$

$$8255 := \frac{8^5 + 2^1 + 5^3 + 5^3}{8^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8255 := \frac{8^5 + 2^1 + 5^3 + 5^3}{8^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8256 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{13} - 5^0 + 6^0}{-8^0 + 2^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$8257 := \frac{8^5 + 2^7 + 5^3 + 7^1}{8^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8257 := \frac{8^5 + 2^7 + 5^3 + 7^1}{8^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8258 := \frac{8^0 + 2^{13} + 5^0 + 8^2}{-8^0 - 2^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$8259 := \frac{8^6 + 2^{20} + 5^8 + 9^1}{8^1 + 2^6 + 5^3 + 9^1}$$

$$8259 := \frac{8^6 + 2^{20} + 5^8 + 9^1}{8^1 + 2^6 + 5^3 + 9^1}$$

$$8260 := \frac{8^5 - 2^{10} + 6^4 + 0^1}{8^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8261 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{13} + 6^1 - 1^0}{8^0 - 2^1 + 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$8262 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{14} + 6^3 + 2^{14}}{8^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8262 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{14} + 6^3 + 2^{14}}{8^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8263 := \frac{8^5 + 2^8 + 6^0 + 3^3}{8^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8263 := \frac{8^5 + 2^8 + 6^0 + 3^3}{8^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8264 := \frac{8^1 + 2^{15} + 6^3 + 4^3}{8^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8264 := \frac{8^1 + 2^{15} + 6^3 + 4^3}{8^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8265 := \frac{-8^1 - 2^7 + 6^5 + 5^4}{8^0 + 2^0 - 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$8266 := \frac{8^3 - 2^4 - 6^1 + 6^5}{8^0 - 2^1 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8267 := \frac{-8^0 + 2^{10} - 6^4 + 7^5}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8268 := \frac{8^7 + 2^7 + 6^5 + 8^9}{8^1 + 2^{13} + 6^5 + 8^3}$$

$$8268 := \frac{8^7 + 2^7 + 6^5 + 8^9}{8^1 + 2^{13} + 6^5 + 8^3}$$

$$8269 := \frac{8^6 + 2^1 + 6^4 + 9^5}{8^0 + 2^0 + 6^2 + 9^0}$$

$$8269 := \frac{8^6 + 2^1 + 6^4 + 9^5}{8^0 + 2^0 + 6^2 + 9^0}$$

$$8270 := \frac{8^5 - 2^5 + 7^3 + 0^0}{8^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8271 := \frac{-8^1 - 2^8 + 7^5 - 1^0}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 1^0}$$

$$8272 := \frac{-8^0 + 2^5 + 7^2 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 2^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8273 := \frac{8^5 + 2^5 + 7^2 + 3^5}{8^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8273 := \frac{8^5 + 2^5 + 7^2 + 3^5}{8^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8274 := \frac{-8^0 - 2^1 + 7^5 - 4^4}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8275 := \frac{8^6 + 2^{19} + 7^7 + 5^7}{8^1 + 2^6 + 7^1 + 5^3}$$

$$8275 := \frac{8^6 + 2^{19} + 7^7 + 5^7}{8^1 + 2^6 + 7^1 + 5^3}$$

$$8276 := \frac{-8^0 + 2^{13} + 7^2 + 6^2}{8^0 + 2^0 - 7^1 + 6^1}$$

$$8277 := \frac{8^3 + 2^{14} + 7^0 - 7^3}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8278 := \frac{-8^0 + 2^1 + 7^3 + 8^5}{8^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8279 := \frac{8^5 + 2^2 + 7^3 + 9^0}{8^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8279 := \frac{8^5 + 2^2 + 7^3 + 9^0}{8^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8282 := \frac{-8^5 - 2^1 + 8^6 + 2^{19}}{-8^0 - 2^2 + 8^2 + 2^5}$$

$$8283 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{12} + 8^4 + 3^3}{-8^0 + 2^0 - 8^1 + 3^2}$$

$$8284 := \frac{-8^1 + 2^7 + 8^2 + 4^7}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8285 := \frac{8^4 - 2^5 + 8^4 + 5^3}{-8^0 - 2^0 + 8^1 - 5^1}$$

$$8286 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{10} + 8^6 + 6^9}{8^3 + 2^3 + 8^3 + 6^3}$$

$$8286 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{10} + 8^6 + 6^9}{8^3 + 2^3 + 8^3 + 6^3}$$

$$8287 := \frac{8^3 + 2^{11} + 8^4 + 7^6}{-8^0 + 2^0 + 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$8288 := \frac{8^2 + 2^8 + 8^2 + 8^5}{8^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8289 := \frac{8^8 + 2^{16} + 8^8 + 9^7}{8^3 + 2^4 + 8^4 + 9^1}$$

$$8290 := \frac{8^7 - 2^9 + 9^3 + 0^0}{-8^0 + 2^8 - 9^0 - 0^0}$$

$$8291 := \frac{8^2 + 2^{16} + 9^3 - 1^0}{-8^0 - 2^0 + 9^1 + 1^0}$$

$$8292 := \frac{8^7 - 2^0 + 9^3 - 2^2}{-8^0 - 2^0 - 9^0 + 2^8}$$

$$8293 := \frac{8^3 + 2^{15} - 9^2 - 3^3}{8^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8294 := \frac{8^0 + 2^5 + 9^5 - 4^5}{8^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$8295 := \frac{-8^0 + 2^{13} + 9^3 - 5^4}{8^0 - 2^1 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8296 := \frac{-8^0 + 2^9 + 9^1 + 6^5}{-8^0 - 2^0 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$8297 := \frac{8^5 + 2^4 + 9^4 + 7^7}{8^1 + 2^3 + 9^2 + 7^1}$$

$$8297 := \frac{8^5 + 2^4 + 9^4 + 7^7}{8^1 + 2^3 + 9^2 + 7^1}$$

$$8299 := \frac{-8^5 - 2^2 - 9^3 + 9^6}{-8^1 - 2^2 - 9^1 + 9^2}$$

$$8302 := \frac{8^7 + 3^6 + 0^0 + 2^{20}}{8^1 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 2^7}$$

$$8302 := \frac{8^7 + 3^6 + 0^0 + 2^{20}}{8^1 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 2^7}$$

$$8303 := \frac{8^5 + 3^7 - 0^0 + 3^8}{8^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 3^1}$$

$$8304 := \frac{-8^0 + 3^{12} + 0^1 + 4^2}{-8^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 4^3}$$

$$8305 := \frac{-8^6 + 3^{13} + 0^0 - 5^7}{8^2 + 3^4 + 0^0 + 5^1}$$

$$8306 := \frac{-8^1 + 3^{14} - 0^0 + 6^4}{8^3 + 3^3 + 0^0 + 6^2}$$

$$8312 := \frac{8^3 + 3^{12} - 1^0 + 2^4}{8^1 - 3^2 + 1^0 + 2^6}$$

$$8313 := \frac{-8^5 - 3^9 - 1^0 + 3^{11}}{8^1 + 3^1 + 1^1 + 3^1}$$

$$8314 := \frac{8^5 + 3^5 + 1^0 - 4^7}{-8^0 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8315 := \frac{-8^2 + 3^5 + 1^0 + 5^8}{-8^1 + 3^4 - 1^0 - 5^2}$$

$$8316 := \frac{8^3 + 3^3 + 1^0 + 6^5}{-8^0 - 3^1 - 1^0 + 6^1}$$

$$8318 := \frac{8^3 - 3^2 + 1^0 + 8^5}{8^0 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8320 := \frac{8^3 - 3^0 + 2^{15} + 0^0}{8^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8321 := \frac{8^3 + 3^1 + 2^{15} + 1^0}{8^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 1^0}$$

$$8321 := \frac{8^3 + 3^1 + 2^{15} + 1^0}{8^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 1^0}$$

$$8322 := \frac{8^0 + 3^0 + 2^7 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 3^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8323 := \frac{8^3 + 3^1 + 2^{15} + 3^2}{8^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8323 := \frac{8^3 + 3^1 + 2^{15} + 3^2}{8^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8324 := \frac{-8^0 + 3^2 + 2^8 + 4^7}{-8^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8325 := \frac{-8^0 + 3^2 + 2^{13} + 5^3}{-8^0 - 3^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$8326 := \frac{8^0 + 3^5 + 2^{19} + 6^1}{8^1 + 3^1 + 2^4 + 6^2}$$

$$8326 := \frac{8^0 + 3^5 + 2^{19} + 6^1}{8^1 + 3^1 + 2^4 + 6^2}$$

$$8327 := \frac{8^3 + 3^3 + 2^{15} + 7^0}{8^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8327 := \frac{8^3 + 3^3 + 2^{15} + 7^0}{8^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8328 := \frac{-8^0 + 3^{10} - 2^{20} + 8^7}{8^0 + 3^1 + 2^7 + 8^0}$$

$$8329 := \frac{8^3 + 3^3 + 2^{15} + 9^1}{8^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8329 := \frac{8^3 + 3^3 + 2^{15} + 9^1}{8^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8331 := \frac{-8^1 - 3^7 + 3^{11} - 1^0}{8^1 + 3^1 + 3^2 + 1^0}$$

$$8332 := \frac{8^2 + 3^0 + 3^{11} + 2^{17}}{8^0 + 3^0 + 3^1 + 2^5}$$

$$8332 := \frac{8^2 + 3^0 + 3^{11} + 2^{17}}{8^0 + 3^0 + 3^1 + 2^5}$$

$$8333 := \frac{8^1 + 3^1 - 3^6 + 3^{10}}{8^1 - 3^0 - 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8334 := \frac{8^7 + 3^1 + 3^{10} + 4^{11}}{8^1 + 3^2 + 3^6 + 4^2}$$

$$8334 := \frac{8^7 + 3^1 + 3^{10} + 4^{11}}{8^1 + 3^2 + 3^6 + 4^2}$$

$$8335 := \frac{8^5 + 3^9 + 3^{14} + 5^8}{8^3 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 5^2}$$

$$8335 := \frac{8^5 + 3^9 + 3^{14} + 5^8}{8^3 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 5^2}$$

$$8336 := \frac{8^5 + 3^2 - 3^6 + 6^4}{8^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8337 := \frac{8^1 + 3^{11} + 3^{12} + 7^2}{8^1 + 3^0 + 3^3 + 7^2}$$

$$8337 := \frac{8^1 + 3^{11} + 3^{12} + 7^2}{8^1 + 3^0 + 3^3 + 7^2}$$

$$8338 := \frac{-8^2 - 3^4 + 3^6 + 8^5}{8^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8339 := \frac{8^7 + 3^5 - 3^8 - 9^6}{-8^2 - 3^0 + 3^5 + 9^1}$$

$$8341 := \frac{8^1 - 3^{12} + 4^{10} - 1^0}{8^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 - 1^0}$$

$$8342 := \frac{8^5 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 2^{17}}{8^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 2^4}$$

$$8342 := \frac{8^5 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 2^{17}}{8^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 2^4}$$

$$8343 := \frac{-8^6 - 3^1 + 4^{10} - 3^7}{8^1 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 3^4}$$

$$8344 := \frac{8^7 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 4^5}{8^0 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 4^1}$$

$$8345 := \frac{8^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^0}{-8^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8346 := \frac{8^0 + 3^0 + 4^9 + 6^6}{8^1 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8346 := \frac{8^0 + 3^0 + 4^9 + 6^6}{8^1 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8347 := \frac{8^4 + 3^{11} + 4^{10} + 7^7}{8^0 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8347 := \frac{8^4 + 3^{11} + 4^{10} + 7^7}{8^0 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8348 := \frac{-8^0 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^7}{8^0 + 3^1 + 4^4 - 8^1}$$

$$8349 := \frac{8^3 - 3^2 + 4^{10} - 9^6}{8^1 - 3^0 + 4^3 - 9^1}$$

$$8350 := \frac{8^1 - 3^9 + 5^7 + 0^1}{8^0 + 3^0 + 5^1 + 0^1}$$

$$8351 := \frac{8^6 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 1^0}{8^1 - 3^0 + 5^2 + 1^0}$$

$$8352 := \frac{8^3 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 2^{15}}{8^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8352 := \frac{8^3 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 2^{15}}{8^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8353 := \frac{8^0 + 3^{10} + 5^{10} + 3^{15}}{8^0 + 3^4 + 5^4 + 3^7}$$

$$8353 := \frac{8^0 + 3^{10} + 5^{10} + 3^{15}}{8^0 + 3^4 + 5^4 + 3^7}$$

$$8354 := \frac{8^7 + 3^0 + 5^2 + 4^7}{8^0 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 4^1}$$

$$8354 := \frac{8^7 + 3^0 + 5^2 + 4^7}{8^0 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 4^1}$$

$$8355 := \frac{-8^2 + 3^{10} + 5^3 - 5^4}{8^1 - 3^0 - 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8356 := \frac{8^5 + 3^4 - 5^1 - 6^5}{-8^0 - 3^0 - 5^0 + 6^1}$$

$$8357 := \frac{8^1 - 3^9 + 5^7 + 7^2}{8^1 - 3^0 - 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8358 := \frac{8^3 + 3^3 + 5^3 + 8^5}{8^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8358 := \frac{8^3 + 3^3 + 5^3 + 8^5}{8^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8359 := \frac{8^5 + 3^7 + 5^8 + 9^3}{8^1 + 3^2 + 5^2 + 9^1}$$

$$8359 := \frac{8^5 + 3^7 + 5^8 + 9^3}{8^1 + 3^2 + 5^2 + 9^1}$$

$$8361 := \frac{8^2 + 3^{10} + 6^5 - 1^0}{-8^0 + 3^2 - 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$8362 := \frac{8^4 + 3^{11} + 6^0 - 2^{17}}{8^0 + 3^1 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8363 := \frac{8^5 - 3^2 - 6^2 + 3^6}{8^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8364 := \frac{-8^0 - 3^5 - 6^5 + 4^7}{-8^0 - 3^0 - 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$8365 := \frac{8^5 + 3^6 - 6^2 - 5^0}{8^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8366 := \frac{-8^4 - 3^6 - 6^0 + 6^6}{-8^0 - 3^0 + 6^0 + 6^1}$$

$$8367 := \frac{8^1 + 3^7 + 6^{10} + 7^8}{8^2 + 3^3 + 6^5 + 7^2}$$

$$8367 := \frac{8^1 + 3^7 + 6^{10} + 7^8}{8^2 + 3^3 + 6^5 + 7^2}$$

$$8368 := \frac{-8^0 + 3^4 + 6^5 + 8^3}{-8^0 - 3^1 + 6^1 - 8^0}$$

$$8369 := \frac{8^5 - 3^3 + 6^1 + 9^3}{8^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8370 := \frac{8^5 + 3^5 + 7^6 + 0^1}{8^1 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 0^1}$$

$$8370 := \frac{8^5 + 3^5 + 7^6 + 0^1}{8^1 + 3^1 + 7^1 + 0^1}$$

$$8371 := \frac{8^6 - 3^7 - 7^6 - 1^0}{8^1 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 1^0}$$

$$8372 := \frac{-8^2 + 3^5 + 7^0 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 3^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8373 := \frac{8^1 + 3^1 + 7^6 - 3^{10}}{8^1 - 3^0 - 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8374 := \frac{8^1 - 3^1 + 7^5 - 4^3}{-8^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8375 := \frac{8^1 + 3^{12} + 7^8 + 5^9}{8^1 + 3^2 + 7^3 + 5^4}$$

$$8375 := \frac{8^1 + 3^{12} + 7^8 + 5^9}{8^1 + 3^2 + 7^3 + 5^4}$$

$$8376 := \frac{8^5 + 3^6 + 7^0 + 6^1}{8^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8377 := \frac{-8^0 - 3^1 - 7^2 + 7^5}{-8^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8378 := \frac{8^1 + 3^6 + 7^1 + 8^5}{8^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8378 := \frac{8^1 + 3^6 + 7^1 + 8^5}{8^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8379 := \frac{8^5 + 3^2 + 7^3 + 9^5}{8^1 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8379 := \frac{8^5 + 3^2 + 7^3 + 9^5}{8^1 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8381 := \frac{8^3 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 1^0}{8^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 1^0}$$

$$8381 := \frac{8^3 + 3^5 + 8^5 + 1^0}{8^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 1^0}$$

$$8382 := \frac{-8^0 + 3^6 + 8^5 + 2^5}{8^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8383 := \frac{8^1 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 3^6}{8^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8383 := \frac{8^1 + 3^3 + 8^5 + 3^6}{8^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8384 := \frac{-8^0 + 3^{16} - 8^6 - 4^5}{-8^1 - 3^2 + 8^4 + 4^5}$$

$$8385 := \frac{-8^2 + 3^8 + 8^5 + 5^7}{-8^0 + 3^2 + 8^0 + 5^1}$$

$$8386 := \frac{8^1 - 3^7 + 8^6 + 6^0}{8^1 + 3^2 + 8^1 + 6^1}$$

$$8387 := \frac{8^3 - 3^9 - 8^5 + 7^7}{8^1 + 3^3 + 8^1 + 7^2}$$

$$8389 := \frac{8^3 - 3^{13} + 8^7 - 9^0}{-8^1 + 3^1 + 8^2 + 9^0}$$

$$8392 := \frac{8^3 - 3^6 + 9^4 + 2^{11}}{-8^0 - 3^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8393 := \frac{8^4 + 3^1 + 9^8 + 3^{15}}{8^1 + 3^3 + 9^4 + 3^5}$$

$$8393 := \frac{8^4 + 3^1 + 9^8 + 3^{15}}{8^1 + 3^3 + 9^4 + 3^5}$$

$$8394 := \frac{8^3 + 3^4 + 9^2 + 4^{10}}{8^0 + 3^3 + 9^2 + 4^2}$$

$$8394 := \frac{8^3 + 3^4 + 9^2 + 4^{10}}{8^0 + 3^3 + 9^2 + 4^2}$$

$$8395 := \frac{8^5 - 3^7 - 9^4 - 5^6}{8^1 - 3^0 - 9^0 - 5^1}$$

$$8396 := \frac{8^5 + 3^4 + 9^3 + 6^1}{8^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8397 := \frac{8^5 + 3^{11} + 9^1 + 7^0}{8^1 + 3^0 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$8397 := \frac{8^5 + 3^{11} + 9^1 + 7^0}{8^1 + 3^0 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$8398 := \frac{8^5 + 3^{10} + 9^6 - 8^6}{-8^0 + 3^3 + 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$8402 := \frac{-8^0 + 4^8 - 0^0 + 2^{18}}{8^1 - 4^0 + 0^1 + 2^5}$$

$$8403 := \frac{-8^5 + 4^{11} + 0^0 - 3^{12}}{8^3 + 4^0 + 0^1 - 3^4}$$

$$8405 := \frac{8^7 + 4^6 + 0^0 + 5^0}{-8^0 + 4^4 + 0^1 - 5^1}$$

$$8406 := \frac{-8^4 + 4^9 + 0^1 + 6^7}{-8^0 + 4^3 + 0^1 + 6^0}$$

$$8407 := \frac{8^1 - 4^0 + 0^1 + 7^5}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 0^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8413 := \frac{8^3 + 4^9 - 1^0 + 3^8}{8^1 - 4^1 + 1^0 + 3^3}$$

$$8415 := \frac{-8^5 - 4^{10} - 1^0 + 5^{10}}{8^1 + 4^5 - 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8422 := \frac{8^7 - 4^3 - 2^1 - 2^3}{-8^0 - 4^1 - 2^1 + 2^8}$$

$$8423 := \frac{8^5 + 4^1 + 2^7 + 3^{12}}{8^0 + 4^0 + 2^6 + 3^0}$$

$$8423 := \frac{8^5 + 4^1 + 2^7 + 3^{12}}{8^0 + 4^0 + 2^6 + 3^0}$$

$$8424 := \frac{-8^1 - 4^2 + 2^{13} + 4^4}{-8^0 - 4^0 - 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$8425 := \frac{-8^4 + 4^9 + 2^1 + 5^5}{8^0 + 4^0 + 2^2 + 5^2}$$

$$8426 := \frac{8^2 + 4^8 + 2^9 + 6^4}{8^0 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$8426 := \frac{8^2 + 4^8 + 2^9 + 6^4}{8^0 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$8427 := \frac{8^5 + 4^9 + 2^5 + 7^0}{8^0 + 4^0 + 2^5 + 7^0}$$

$$8427 := \frac{8^5 + 4^9 + 2^5 + 7^0}{8^0 + 4^0 + 2^5 + 7^0}$$

$$8428 := \frac{8^2 + 4^1 + 2^{15} + 8^6}{8^0 + 4^0 + 2^5 + 8^0}$$

$$8428 := \frac{8^2 + 4^1 + 2^{15} + 8^6}{8^0 + 4^0 + 2^5 + 8^0}$$

$$8429 := \frac{8^0 - 4^4 + 2^{14} + 9^3}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8432 := \frac{8^0 - 4^1 + 3^5 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 4^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8433 := \frac{8^5 + 4^9 + 3^4 + 3^{12}}{8^2 + 4^2 + 3^2 + 3^2}$$

$$8433 := \frac{8^5 + 4^9 + 3^4 + 3^{12}}{8^2 + 4^2 + 3^2 + 3^2}$$

$$8434 := \frac{-8^0 + 4^6 + 3^5 + 4^6}{-8^0 - 4^0 - 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$8435 := \frac{8^3 + 4^{13} + 3^6 + 5^6}{8^1 + 4^6 + 3^6 + 5^5}$$

$$8435 := \frac{8^3 + 4^{13} + 3^6 + 5^6}{8^1 + 4^6 + 3^6 + 5^5}$$

$$8436 := \frac{8^0 + 4^0 + 3^{10} + 6^0}{8^0 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8437 := \frac{8^1 + 4^0 + 3^{10} + 7^0}{8^0 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8437 := \frac{8^1 + 4^0 + 3^{10} + 7^0}{8^0 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8438 := \frac{8^1 + 4^0 + 3^{10} + 8^1}{8^0 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8438 := \frac{8^1 + 4^0 + 3^{10} + 8^1}{8^0 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8439 := \frac{8^5 + 4^2 + 3^5 + 9^3}{8^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8439 := \frac{8^5 + 4^2 + 3^5 + 9^3}{8^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8440 := \frac{8^3 - 4^2 + 4^7 + 0^1}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8442 := \frac{-8^1 - 4^1 + 4^7 + 2^9}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8443 := \frac{8^2 + 4^7 + 4^9 + 3^3}{8^0 + 4^0 + 4^1 + 3^3}$$

$$8444 := \frac{8^4 - 4^1 + 4^4 + 4^6}{-8^0 - 4^0 - 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$8445 := \frac{8^3 - 4^0 + 4^7 - 5^1}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8446 := \frac{-8^3 - 4^5 + 4^9 + 6^7}{8^1 + 4^1 + 4^2 + 6^2}$$

$$8447 := \frac{8^4 + 4^4 + 4^6 - 7^0}{-8^0 - 4^0 + 4^1 - 7^0}$$

$$8448 := \frac{8^3 + 4^4 + 4^4 + 8^5}{8^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8448 := \frac{8^3 + 4^4 + 4^4 + 8^5}{8^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8448 := \frac{8^5 + 4^5 + 4^5 + 8^5}{8^1 + 4^1 + 4^1 - 8^1}$$

$$8449 := \frac{8^4 + 4^4 + 4^6 + 9^0}{-8^0 - 4^0 + 4^1 - 9^0}$$

$$8450 := \frac{8^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 0^0}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8451 := \frac{8^9 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 1^0}{8^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 1^0}$$

$$8451 := \frac{8^9 + 4^8 + 5^5 + 1^0}{8^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 1^0}$$

$$8452 := \frac{-8^0 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 4^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8453 := \frac{8^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 3^{10}}{8^1 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 3^0}$$

$$8453 := \frac{8^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 3^{10}}{8^1 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 3^0}$$

$$8454 := \frac{8^5 - 4^0 + 5^2 + 4^5}{8^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8455 := \frac{8^0 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 5^9}{-8^0 + 4^4 + 5^0 - 5^2}$$

$$8456 := \frac{-8^1 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^4}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8457 := \frac{8^3 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^5}{8^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8457 := \frac{8^3 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^5}{8^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8458 := \frac{8^0 + 4^{14} - 5^{12} + 8^8}{8^0 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 8^4}$$

$$8459 := \frac{8^5 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^2}{8^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8460 := \frac{8^1 + 4^6 + 6^6 + 0^1}{8^0 + 4^1 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$8460 := \frac{8^1 + 4^6 + 6^6 + 0^1}{8^0 + 4^1 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$8461 := \frac{-8^4 - 4^4 + 6^6 + 1^0}{-8^0 - 4^0 + 6^1 + 1^0}$$

$$8462 := \frac{8^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 2^{17}}{8^0 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 2^3}$$

$$8462 := \frac{8^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 2^{17}}{8^0 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 2^3}$$

$$8463 := \frac{-8^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 3^8}{-8^0 - 4^0 + 6^1 - 3^1}$$

$$8464 := \frac{8^1 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 4^9}{8^1 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 4^2}$$

$$8464 := \frac{8^1 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 4^9}{8^1 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 4^2}$$

$$8465 := \frac{8^1 + 4^0 + 6^4 + 5^6}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8466 := \frac{8^5 + 4^5 + 6^2 + 6^2}{8^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8466 := \frac{8^5 + 4^5 + 6^2 + 6^2}{8^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8467 := \frac{8^2 + 4^3 - 6^0 + 7^5}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8468 := \frac{8^2 - 4^4 + 6^4 + 8^5}{8^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8469 := \frac{8^3 + 4^9 - 6^2 - 9^2}{8^1 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 9^0}$$

$$8472 := \frac{8^0 - 4^3 + 7^3 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 4^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8473 := \frac{8^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 3^0}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8474 := \frac{-8^0 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 4^{11}}{8^1 + 4^3 + 7^5 - 4^7}$$

$$8475 := \frac{8^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 5^1}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8476 := \frac{-8^1 + 4^5 + 7^6 - 6^0}{8^1 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8477 := \frac{-8^3 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 7^8}{-8^1 + 4^5 + 7^1 - 7^3}$$

$$8479 := \frac{-8^0 + 4^4 + 7^2 + 9^5}{8^0 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8480 := \frac{8^2 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 0^1}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8481 := \frac{8^3 + 4^4 + 8^6 - 1^0}{8^1 + 4^2 + 8^1 - 1^0}$$

$$8482 := \frac{8^1 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 2^7}{8^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8482 := \frac{8^1 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 2^7}{8^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8483 := \frac{8^0 - 4^5 + 8^5 + 3^7}{8^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8484 := \frac{8^1 + 4^3 + 8^3 + 4^7}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8485 := \frac{8^2 + 4^9 + 8^3 + 5^8}{8^1 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 5^0}$$

$$8485 := \frac{8^2 + 4^9 + 8^3 + 5^8}{8^1 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 5^0}$$

$$8486 := \frac{-8^2 + 4^5 + 8^5 + 6^3}{8^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8487 := \frac{-8^2 + 4^5 + 8^6 - 7^1}{-8^0 - 4^2 - 8^0 + 7^2}$$

$$8489 := \frac{8^0 + 4^7 + 8^3 + 9^2}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8490 := \frac{-8^6 - 4^8 + 9^6 - 0^0}{-8^0 + 4^2 + 9^1 + 0^1}$$

$$8492 := \frac{-8^0 + 4^7 + 9^3 - 2^7}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8493 := \frac{8^8 + 4^{12} + 9^0 + 3^{14}}{8^4 + 4^4 + 9^2 + 3^4}$$

$$8493 := \frac{8^8 + 4^{12} + 9^0 + 3^{14}}{8^4 + 4^4 + 9^2 + 3^4}$$

$$8494 := \frac{-8^7 + 4^0 + 9^8 + 4^1}{-8^1 + 4^1 + 9^3 + 4^6}$$

$$8495 := \frac{8^1 + 4^4 + 9^4 + 5^7}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$8496 := \frac{-8^1 - 4^0 + 9^3 + 6^5}{-8^0 - 4^0 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$8497 := \frac{8^5 + 4^5 + 9^1 - 7^5}{-8^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8498 := \frac{-8^0 + 4^8 - 9^4 + 8^3}{8^0 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8499 := \frac{-8^4 + 4^8 - 9^1 + 9^4}{-8^0 - 4^0 + 9^0 + 9^1}$$

$$8502 := \frac{8^7 + 5^1 + 0^0 - 2^{19}}{8^2 + 5^3 + 0^1 - 2^2}$$

$$8503 := \frac{8^3 + 5^8 + 0^1 + 3^0}{8^0 + 5^3 + 0^0 - 3^4}$$

$$8504 := \frac{-8^0 + 5^4 + 0^1 + 4^7}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8505 := \frac{8^6 + 5^3 + 0^0 - 5^6}{-8^0 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 5^2}$$

$$8506 := \frac{-8^5 + 5^5 - 0^0 + 6^6}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8507 := \frac{8^6 + 5^3 - 0^0 - 7^6}{8^1 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 7^1}$$

$$8509 := \frac{8^3 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 9^5}{8^0 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 9^0}$$

$$8509 := \frac{8^3 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 9^5}{8^0 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 9^0}$$

$$8512 := \frac{8^9 - 5^0 + 1^0 - 2^9}{8^1 - 5^4 + 1^0 + 2^{14}}$$

$$8514 := \frac{-8^5 + 5^{10} - 1^0 - 4^{10}}{-8^1 + 5^1 - 1^0 + 4^5}$$

$$8516 := \frac{8^4 + 5^5 - 1^0 + 6^4}{-8^0 - 5^1 + 1^0 + 6^1}$$

$$8520 := \frac{-8^5 + 5^8 - 2^4 - 0^0}{8^0 + 5^2 + 2^4 + 0^1}$$

$$8522 := \frac{-8^0 + 5^8 + 2^{11} + 2^{14}}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 2^4 + 2^5}$$

$$8523 := \frac{8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 3^8}{8^0 + 5^1 + 2^0 + 3^1}$$

$$8523 := \frac{8^3 + 5^7 + 2^5 + 3^8}{8^0 + 5^1 + 2^0 + 3^1}$$

$$8524 := \frac{-8^0 + 5^5 - 2^{10} + 4^9}{8^0 + 5^2 + 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$8525 := \frac{8^3 + 5^4 + 2^{19} + 5^5}{8^1 + 5^2 + 2^2 + 5^2}$$

$$8525 := \frac{8^3 + 5^4 + 2^{19} + 5^5}{8^1 + 5^2 + 2^2 + 5^2}$$

$$8526 := \frac{8^0 + 5^0 + 2^2 + 6^8}{8^1 + 5^2 + 2^7 + 6^2}$$

$$8526 := \frac{8^0 + 5^0 + 2^2 + 6^8}{8^1 + 5^2 + 2^7 + 6^2}$$

$$8527 := \frac{-8^1 - 5^0 + 2^8 + 7^5}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8529 := \frac{8^7 + 5^3 + 2^7 + 9^3}{8^1 + 5^3 + 2^5 + 9^2}$$

$$8529 := \frac{8^7 + 5^3 + 2^7 + 9^3}{8^1 + 5^3 + 2^5 + 9^2}$$

$$8530 := \frac{8^5 + 5^7 - 3^1 + 0^1}{8^1 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 0^0}$$

$$8531 := \frac{8^5 + 5^7 + 3^2 + 1^0}{8^1 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 1^0}$$

$$8531 := \frac{8^5 + 5^7 + 3^2 + 1^0}{8^1 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 1^0}$$

$$8532 := \frac{8^5 + 5^7 + 3^{11} + 2^{11}}{8^0 + 5^1 + 3^3 + 2^0}$$

$$8532 := \frac{8^5 + 5^7 + 3^{11} + 2^{11}}{8^0 + 5^1 + 3^3 + 2^0}$$

$$8533 := \frac{8^5 + 5^7 + 3^2 + 3^3}{8^1 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 3^1}$$

$$8533 := \frac{8^5 + 5^7 + 3^2 + 3^3}{8^1 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 3^1}$$

$$8534 := \frac{8^1 + 5^8 + 3^9 + 4^7}{8^1 + 5^2 + 3^0 + 4^2}$$

$$8534 := \frac{8^1 + 5^8 + 3^9 + 4^7}{8^1 + 5^2 + 3^0 + 4^2}$$

$$8535 := \frac{-8^2 - 5^6 + 3^2 + 5^9}{8^1 + 5^0 + 3^5 - 5^2}$$

$$8536 := \frac{8^5 + 5^5 + 3^1 + 6^7}{8^1 + 5^0 + 3^3 + 6^0}$$

$$8537 := \frac{8^5 + 5^7 + 3^4 + 7^1}{8^1 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 7^0}$$

$$8537 := \frac{8^5 + 5^7 + 3^4 + 7^1}{8^1 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 7^0}$$

$$8538 := \frac{-8^2 - 5^6 - 3^1 + 8^5}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8539 := \frac{-8^4 + 5^1 + 3^{13} + 9^4}{8^1 + 5^3 - 3^3 + 9^2}$$

$$8540 := \frac{8^5 - 5^6 - 4^3 + 0^0}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8542 := \frac{-8^0 + 5^8 - 4^9 + 2^{13}}{8^1 + 5^1 + 4^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8543 := \frac{8^0 + 5^2 + 4^{10} + 3^7}{8^0 + 5^2 + 4^2 + 3^4}$$

$$8543 := \frac{8^0 + 5^2 + 4^{10} + 3^7}{8^0 + 5^2 + 4^2 + 3^4}$$

$$8544 := \frac{8^0 - 5^8 - 4^3 + 4^{10}}{8^1 + 5^0 + 4^1 + 4^3}$$

$$8545 := \frac{8^4 - 5^3 + 4^9 - 5^7}{8^1 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 5^1}$$

$$8546 := \frac{-8^0 + 5^9 - 4^2 + 6^6}{8^0 + 5^0 + 4^2 + 6^3}$$

$$8547 := \frac{8^5 + 5^7 + 4^9 + 7^7}{8^2 + 5^1 + 4^3 + 7^1}$$

$$8547 := \frac{8^5 + 5^7 + 4^9 + 7^7}{8^2 + 5^1 + 4^3 + 7^1}$$

$$8548 := \frac{8^0 - 5^1 - 4^8 + 8^6}{8^0 + 5^1 + 4^2 + 8^0}$$

$$8549 := \frac{8^1 + 5^4 + 4^7 + 9^2}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 9^0}$$

$$8552 := \frac{-8^2 + 5^2 - 5^6 + 2^{15}}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8553 := \frac{-8^3 + 5^0 + 5^6 - 3^8}{-8^1 - 5^0 + 5^0 + 3^2}$$

$$8554 := \frac{8^3 - 5^5 + 5^6 + 4^6}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8555 := \frac{8^8 - 5^0 + 5^4 + 5^6}{-8^3 - 5^2 - 5^4 + 5^5}$$

$$8556 := \frac{8^5 + 5^1 - 5^6 - 6^2}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8557 := \frac{8^5 + 5^1 + 5^7 + 7^3}{8^1 - 5^0 - 5^0 + 7^1}$$

$$8558 := \frac{-8^5 - 5^1 - 5^9 + 8^7}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$8559 := \frac{-8^3 + 5^4 + 5^{10} + 9^2}{8^3 + 5^1 + 5^4 - 9^0}$$

$$8562 := \frac{8^0 + 5^8 + 6^5 + 2^{20}}{8^2 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 2^6}$$

$$8562 := \frac{8^0 + 5^8 + 6^5 + 2^{20}}{8^2 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 2^6}$$

$$8563 := \frac{8^4 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 3^0}{8^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$$

$$8563 := \frac{8^4 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 3^0}{8^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$$

$$8564 := \frac{8^5 - 5^6 + 6^0 - 4^2}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8565 := \frac{-8^6 - 5^1 - 6^0 + 5^8}{8^1 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 5^1}$$

$$8567 := \frac{-8^2 + 5^9 + 6^3 - 7^0}{8^1 + 5^1 + 6^3 - 7^0}$$

$$8568 := \frac{-8^0 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8569 := \frac{8^5 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 9^7}{8^3 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 9^1}$$

$$8569 := \frac{8^5 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 9^7}{8^3 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 9^1}$$

$$8570 := \frac{-8^7 + 5^2 + 7^9 + 0^1}{8^4 + 5^2 + 7^3 + 0^1}$$

$$8572 := \frac{8^3 - 5^3 - 7^1 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 5^0 + 7^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8573 := \frac{8^3 + 5^0 - 7^6 + 3^{11}}{8^1 - 5^0 - 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8574 := \frac{8^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 4^1}{8^1 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 4^2}$$

$$8574 := \frac{8^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 4^1}{8^1 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 4^2}$$

$$8576 := \frac{-8^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 - 6^3}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8577 := \frac{-8^0 + 5^1 + 7^3 + 7^5}{-8^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8578 := \frac{-8^3 + 5^8 - 7^1 - 8^4}{-8^0 + 5^1 + 7^2 - 8^1}$$

$$8579 := \frac{8^6 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 9^3}{-8^1 - 5^0 + 7^2 - 9^1}$$

$$8582 := \frac{8^0 - 5^5 + 8^5 + 2^{18}}{8^0 + 5^0 + 8^2 - 2^5}$$

$$8583 := \frac{8^5 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 3^1}{8^0 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8583 := \frac{8^5 + 5^5 + 8^5 + 3^1}{8^0 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8585 := \frac{8^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 + 5^8}{8^1 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$8585 := \frac{8^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 + 5^8}{8^1 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$8586 := \frac{-8^0 + 5^9 - 8^4 - 6^1}{8^1 - 5^1 + 8^1 + 6^3}$$

$$8587 := \frac{8^6 + 5^{11} + 8^6 - 7^8}{8^3 + 5^3 + 8^4 + 7^3}$$

$$8589 := \frac{-8^3 + 5^0 - 8^5 + 9^6}{8^0 - 5^2 + 8^0 + 9^2}$$

$$8592 := \frac{8^1 - 5^2 + 9^4 + 2^{11}}{-8^0 - 5^0 + 9^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8593 := \frac{-8^7 + 5^9 - 9^3 + 3^{12}}{8^1 + 5^0 + 9^1 + 3^3}$$

$$8594 := \frac{8^1 - 5^3 + 9^1 + 4^{10}}{-8^0 + 5^3 - 9^0 - 4^0}$$

$$8595 := \frac{-8^2 - 5^4 - 9^2 + 5^7}{8^1 - 5^0 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8596 := \frac{-8^2 + 5^8 - 9^5 - 6^7}{-8^0 - 5^0 + 9^1 - 6^0}$$

$$8597 := \frac{8^3 + 5^4 + 9^5 - 7^1}{8^1 - 5^0 - 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8598 := \frac{-8^3 + 5^2 + 9^5 - 8^5}{8^0 + 5^0 + 9^1 - 8^1}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 8599 := \frac{8^5 + 5^7 - 9^4 + 9^5}{8^1 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 9^1} & 8628 := \frac{8^5 + 6^5 + 2^{11} + 8^7}{8^1 + 6^3 + 2^4 + 8^1} & 8643 := \frac{8^7 + 6^3 + 4^9 + 3^3}{8^1 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 3^5} \\
 8603 := \frac{8^7 + 6^2 - 0^0 - 3^{12}}{8^2 + 6^2 + 0^0 + 3^4} & 8628 := \frac{8^5 + 6^5 + 2^{11} + 8^7}{8^1 + 6^3 + 2^4 + 8^1} & 8643 := \frac{8^7 + 6^3 + 4^9 + 3^3}{8^1 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 3^5} \\
 8604 := \frac{-8^3 + 6^7 + 0^1 - 4^6}{-8^0 + 6^2 + 0^0 - 4^1} & 8629 := \frac{8^7 + 6^6 + 2^{15} + 9^4}{8^1 + 6^2 + 2^7 + 9^2} & 8644 := \frac{8^3 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 4^7}{8^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 4^0} \\
 8607 := \frac{8^4 + 6^7 + 0^1 - 7^0}{-8^0 + 6^2 - 0^0 - 7^0} & 8629 := \frac{8^7 + 6^6 + 2^{15} + 9^4}{8^1 + 6^2 + 2^7 + 9^2} & 8644 := \frac{8^3 + 6^4 + 4^7 + 4^7}{8^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 4^0} \\
 8613 := \frac{8^6 - 6^4 - 1^0 - 3^9}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 1^0 + 3^3} & 8630 := \frac{8^2 + 6^4 + 3^{10} + 0^0}{-8^0 - 6^0 + 3^2 + 0^1} & 8645 := \frac{8^1 + 6^7 + 4^8 + 5^7}{8^1 + 6^2 + 4^1 + 5^0} \\
 8619 := \frac{-8^3 - 6^8 - 1^0 + 9^7}{8^2 + 6^3 - 1^0 + 9^2} & 8631 := \frac{8^3 - 6^5 + 3^{10} + 1^0}{8^0 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 1^0} & 8645 := \frac{8^1 + 6^7 + 4^8 + 5^7}{8^1 + 6^2 + 4^1 + 5^0} \\
 8620 := \frac{-8^0 + 6^7 - 2^{12} + 0^0}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 2^5 + 0^1} & 8632 := \frac{-8^0 + 6^5 + 3^6 + 2^7}{-8^0 - 6^0 + 3^0 + 2^1} & 8646 := \frac{8^9 + 6^1 + 4^9 + 6^1}{8^0 + 6^5 + 4^0 + 6^5} \\
 8622 := \frac{8^2 + 6^{11} + 2^8 + 2^{14}}{8^3 + 6^5 + 2^{10} + 2^{15}} & 8633 := \frac{8^3 + 6^5 + 3^8 + 3^9}{8^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 3^0} & 8646 := \frac{8^9 + 6^1 + 4^9 + 6^1}{8^0 + 6^5 + 4^0 + 6^5} \\
 8622 := \frac{8^2 + 6^{11} + 2^8 + 2^{14}}{8^3 + 6^5 + 2^{10} + 2^{15}} & 8633 := \frac{8^3 + 6^5 + 3^8 + 3^9}{8^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 3^0} & 8647 := \frac{8^3 + 6^5 + 4^2 + 7^3}{-8^0 - 6^0 + 4^1 - 7^0} \\
 8623 := \frac{8^1 + 6^4 + 2^3 + 3^{10}}{8^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 3^1} & 8634 := \frac{8^0 + 6^9 + 3^0 + 4^{11}}{8^3 + 6^2 + 3^4 + 4^5} & 8648 := \frac{8^3 + 6^4 + 4^2 + 8^5}{8^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 8^0} \\
 8623 := \frac{8^1 + 6^4 + 2^3 + 3^{10}}{8^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 3^1} & 8634 := \frac{8^0 + 6^9 + 3^0 + 4^{11}}{8^3 + 6^2 + 3^4 + 4^5} & 8648 := \frac{8^3 + 6^4 + 4^2 + 8^5}{8^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 8^0} \\
 8624 := \frac{8^7 + 6^4 + 2^{17} + 4^6}{8^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 4^4} & 8635 := \frac{8^3 - 6^5 + 3^{10} + 5^2}{8^0 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 5^0} & 8649 := \frac{8^3 + 6^9 + 4^9 + 9^6}{8^1 + 6^3 + 4^5 + 9^1} \\
 8624 := \frac{8^7 + 6^4 + 2^{17} + 4^6}{8^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 4^4} & 8636 := \frac{8^7 - 6^0 - 3^{10} - 6^1}{-8^0 - 6^1 + 3^3 + 6^3} & 8649 := \frac{8^3 + 6^9 + 4^9 + 9^6}{8^1 + 6^3 + 4^5 + 9^1} \\
 8625 := \frac{8^7 + 6^5 + 2^{13} + 5^1}{8^1 + 6^3 + 2^4 + 5^1} & 8637 := \frac{8^1 + 6^3 + 3^5 + 7^5}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 7^0} & 8652 := \frac{-8^3 - 6^0 + 5^7 + 2^8}{8^0 + 6^0 + 5^1 + 2^1} \\
 8625 := \frac{8^7 + 6^5 + 2^{13} + 5^1}{8^1 + 6^3 + 2^4 + 5^1} & 8639 := \frac{8^6 + 6^2 + 3^3 + 9^7}{8^3 + 6^2 + 3^3 + 9^1} & 8653 := \frac{-8^3 + 6^1 + 5^6 + 3^7}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 3^0} \\
 8626 := \frac{8^6 + 6^3 + 2^{20} + 6^3}{8^2 + 6^2 + 2^4 + 6^2} & 8639 := \frac{8^6 + 6^2 + 3^3 + 9^7}{8^3 + 6^2 + 3^3 + 9^1} & 8654 := \frac{8^7 - 6^7 + 5^3 - 4^0}{-8^0 + 6^3 - 5^0 - 4^1} \\
 8626 := \frac{8^6 + 6^3 + 2^{20} + 6^3}{8^2 + 6^2 + 2^4 + 6^2} & 8640 := \frac{-8^3 + 6^7 - 4^9 + 0^1}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 0^0} & 8655 := \frac{8^6 + 6^1 + 5^4 - 5^5}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 5^1 + 5^2} \\
 8627 := \frac{8^3 + 6^5 - 2^2 + 7^3}{-8^0 - 6^0 + 2^1 + 7^0} & 8642 := \frac{-8^3 + 6^7 + 4^1 - 2^{18}}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 2^0} & 8656 := \frac{8^0 - 6^1 + 5^7 - 6^3}{8^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 6^1}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 8657 := \frac{8^3 + 6^7 + 5^3 + 7^6}{8^1 + 6^1 + 5^2 + 7^1} & 8679 := \frac{8^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 9^4}{8^0 + 6^2 - 7^1 + 9^0} & 8702 := \frac{8^3 - 7^0 - 0^0 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 7^0 + 0^0 + 2^1} \\
 8657 := \frac{8^3 + 6^7 + 5^3 + 7^6}{8^1 + 6^1 + 5^2 + 7^1} & 8682 := \frac{8^2 + 6^5 + 8^6 - 2^{17}}{8^0 + 6^1 + 8^0 + 2^3} & 8703 := \frac{8^6 + 7^7 + 0^0 + 3^7}{8^3 + 7^3 - 0^0 - 3^6} \\
 8658 := \frac{8^0 - 6^7 + 5^8 - 8^5}{8^0 + 6^1 + 5^0 + 8^0} & 8683 := \frac{8^4 - 6^5 - 8^6 + 3^{13}}{-8^1 + 6^3 - 8^2 + 3^2} & 8704 := \frac{8^4 - 7^0 + 0^0 + 4^8}{-8^0 + 7^1 + 0^0 + 4^0} \\
 8659 := \frac{-8^5 + 6^2 + 5^7 + 9^4}{-8^0 - 6^0 - 5^0 + 9^1} & 8684 := \frac{-8^3 + 6^7 - 8^3 - 4^5}{-8^0 + 6^2 + 8^0 - 4^1} & 8705 := \frac{8^4 + 7^6 + 0^1 + 5^3}{8^0 + 7^1 + 0^0 + 5^1} \\
 8662 := \frac{8^3 - 6^1 - 6^2 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 6^0 + 6^0 + 2^1} & 8685 := \frac{-8^1 + 6^3 - 8^1 + 5^8}{-8^1 - 6^1 + 8^2 - 5^1} & 8705 := \frac{8^4 + 7^6 + 0^1 + 5^3}{8^0 + 7^1 + 0^0 + 5^1} \\
 8663 := \frac{8^3 - 6^3 + 6^4 + 3^{10}}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 6^1 + 3^0} & 8688 := \frac{-8^5 + 6^6 - 8^5 + 8^6}{-8^0 + 6^2 + 8^0 - 8^1} & 8712 := \frac{8^3 + 7^1 + 1^0 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 7^0 + 1^0 + 2^1} \\
 8664 := \frac{8^3 + 6^3 + 6^3 + 4^7}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 4^0} & 8689 := \frac{8^0 + 6^{10} - 8^4 - 9^7}{-8^0 - 6^3 + 8^2 + 9^4} & 8715 := \frac{-8^0 + 7^5 - 1^0 + 5^4}{-8^0 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 5^0} \\
 8665 := \frac{8^5 + 6^5 + 6^7 + 5^3}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 6^2 + 5^0} & 8691 := \frac{8^6 - 6^6 - 9^5 - 1^0}{-8^1 + 6^2 - 9^1 - 1^0} & 8719 := \frac{8^5 - 7^2 - 1^0 - 9^4}{-8^1 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 9^1} \\
 8666 := \frac{-8^6 - 6^6 + 6^8 + 6^8}{8^2 + 6^2 + 6^2 + 6^3} & 8692 := \frac{8^0 + 6^7 + 9^5 + 2^1}{8^0 + 6^2 + 9^0 + 2^0} & 8720 := \frac{-8^2 + 7^6 + 2^{16} - 0^0}{-8^0 + 7^1 + 2^4 - 0^0} \\
 8667 := \frac{8^3 + 6^2 + 6^5 + 7^3}{-8^0 + 6^0 - 6^1 + 7^1} & 8692 := \frac{8^0 + 6^7 + 9^5 + 2^1}{8^0 + 6^2 + 9^0 + 2^0} & 8721 := \frac{-8^3 - 7^0 + 2^{18} - 1^0}{8^1 + 7^1 + 2^4 - 1^0} \\
 8668 := \frac{8^6 + 6^5 - 6^6 + 8^6}{-8^0 - 6^0 - 6^1 + 8^2} & 8693 := \frac{8^5 + 6^7 + 9^0 + 3^5}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 3^3} & 8723 := \frac{8^5 + 7^2 + 2^{11} + 3^3}{8^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 3^0} \\
 8669 := \frac{-8^0 + 6^5 + 6^7 + 9^5}{-8^0 + 6^1 + 6^2 - 9^0} & 8694 := \frac{8^3 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 4^0}{8^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 4^1} & 8723 := \frac{8^5 + 7^2 + 2^{11} + 3^3}{8^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 3^0} \\
 8672 := \frac{8^5 - 6^0 + 7^4 + 2^{13}}{8^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 2^1} & 8694 := \frac{8^3 + 6^4 + 9^5 + 4^0}{8^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 4^1} & 8724 := \frac{8^3 + 7^5 + 2^7 + 4^0}{-8^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 4^0} \\
 8673 := \frac{8^3 + 6^2 + 7^5 - 3^2}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 3^0} & 8695 := \frac{8^6 - 6^4 + 9^0 + 5^0}{8^1 + 6^1 - 9^1 + 5^2} & 8725 := \frac{-8^2 + 7^4 - 2^9 + 5^6}{-8^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 5^0} \\
 8674 := \frac{8^6 - 6^0 - 7^2 + 4^{13}}{-8^0 + 6^5 - 7^1 - 4^0} & 8696 := \frac{-8^2 - 6^0 + 9^6 + 6^5}{-8^0 + 6^2 - 9^1 + 6^2} & 8726 := \frac{-8^0 + 7^2 + 2^{16} + 6^8}{8^2 + 7^1 + 2^7 + 6^0} \\
 8675 := \frac{8^3 + 6^1 + 7^5 + 5^2}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 5^0} & 8697 := \frac{8^3 - 6^1 + 9^2 + 7^5}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 7^0} & 8727 := \frac{8^3 + 7^1 + 2^7 + 7^5}{-8^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 7^0} \\
 8677 := \frac{8^3 + 6^2 - 7^0 + 7^5}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 7^0} & 8698 := \frac{-8^0 + 6^4 + 9^3 + 8^5}{8^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 8^0} & 8728 := \frac{-8^0 + 7^4 - 2^8 + 8^5}{8^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 8^0} \\
 8678 := \frac{8^0 + 6^2 + 7^5 + 8^3}{-8^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 8^0} & 8699 := \frac{-8^8 - 6^1 - 9^7 + 9^8}{-8^4 + 6^1 - 9^0 + 9^4} & 8729 := \frac{-8^0 + 7^1 + 2^{11} + 9^5}{8^0 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 9^0}
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 8730 := \frac{8^6 - 7^0 - 3^5 + 0^1}{8^0 + 7^0 + 3^3 + 0^0} & 8745 := \frac{8^5 + 7^3 + 4^1 - 5^6}{-8^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 5^0} & 8765 := \frac{8^3 + 7^5 + 6^3 - 5^1}{-8^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 5^0} \\
 8732 := \frac{8^6 + 7^6 + 3^1 + 2^{16}}{8^0 + 7^1 + 3^3 + 2^4} & 8746 := \frac{-8^0 + 7^6 - 4^5 - 6^6}{-8^0 - 7^0 + 4^1 + 6^1} & 8767 := \frac{8^3 + 7^1 + 6^2 + 7^7}{8^1 + 7^0 + 6^2 + 7^2} \\
 8732 := \frac{8^6 + 7^6 + 3^1 + 2^{16}}{8^0 + 7^1 + 3^3 + 2^4} & 8747 := \frac{8^1 + 7^8 + 4^{10} + 7^8}{8^2 + 7^1 + 4^5 + 7^3} & 8767 := \frac{8^3 + 7^1 + 6^2 + 7^7}{8^1 + 7^0 + 6^2 + 7^2} \\
 8733 := \frac{-8^1 - 7^1 + 3^7 + 3^8}{-8^1 - 7^0 + 3^0 + 3^2} & 8747 := \frac{8^1 + 7^8 + 4^{10} + 7^8}{8^2 + 7^1 + 4^5 + 7^3} & 8768 := \frac{8^0 + 7^5 + 6^3 + 8^3}{-8^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 8^0} \\
 8734 := \frac{-8^2 + 7^5 + 3^6 - 4^1}{-8^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 4^0} & 8749 := \frac{8^{10} + 7^0 + 4^7 + 9^4}{8^4 + 7^6 + 4^4 + 9^3} & 8769 := \frac{8^1 + 7^7 + 6^1 + 9^3}{8^1 + 7^2 + 6^2 + 9^0} \\
 8735 := \frac{8^0 - 7^3 + 3^7 + 5^6}{-8^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 5^0} & 8749 := \frac{8^{10} + 7^0 + 4^7 + 9^4}{8^4 + 7^6 + 4^4 + 9^3} & 8769 := \frac{8^1 + 7^7 + 6^1 + 9^3}{8^1 + 7^2 + 6^2 + 9^0} \\
 8736 := \frac{8^5 + 7^1 - 3^8 - 6^1}{-8^0 - 7^0 - 3^0 + 6^1} & 8752 := \frac{-8^2 - 7^0 + 5^4 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 7^0 + 5^0 + 2^1} & 8771 := \frac{8^7 + 7^2 + 7^7 - 1^0}{-8^1 - 7^0 + 7^3 - 1^0} \\
 8737 := \frac{8^3 + 7^5 + 3^{10} + 7^7}{8^1 + 7^1 + 3^4 + 7^1} & 8753 := \frac{8^4 + 7^1 + 5^6 + 3^{10}}{8^1 - 7^0 + 5^0 + 3^0} & 8772 := \frac{8^3 + 7^0 + 7^7 + 2^9}{8^2 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 2^4} \\
 8737 := \frac{8^3 + 7^5 + 3^{10} + 7^7}{8^1 + 7^1 + 3^4 + 7^1} & 8754 := \frac{8^1 + 7^3 + 5^3 + 4^9}{8^1 + 7^0 + 5^1 + 4^2} & 8772 := \frac{8^3 + 7^0 + 7^7 + 2^9}{8^2 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 2^4} \\
 8738 := \frac{-8^3 + 7^4 + 3^9 - 8^4}{-8^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 8^0} & 8754 := \frac{8^1 + 7^3 + 5^3 + 4^9}{8^1 + 7^0 + 5^1 + 4^2} & 8773 := \frac{-8^4 - 7^5 + 7^6 - 3^5}{8^1 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 3^0} \\
 8739 := \frac{-8^1 - 7^0 + 3^7 + 9^4}{-8^1 - 7^0 + 3^0 + 9^1} & 8755 := \frac{-8^1 - 7^5 - 5^2 + 5^7}{8^1 - 7^0 - 5^0 + 5^0} & 8774 := \frac{8^6 + 7^1 - 7^6 - 4^8}{-8^0 - 7^0 + 7^1 + 4^1} \\
 8740 := \frac{8^1 + 7^2 + 4^9 - 0^0}{8^1 + 7^1 + 4^2 - 0^0} & 8756 := \frac{8^3 + 7^1 + 5^8 + 6^6}{8^1 + 7^0 + 5^1 + 6^2} & 8775 := \frac{-8^6 + 7^4 - 7^5 + 5^8}{8^1 - 7^0 + 7^0 + 5^1} \\
 8741 := \frac{8^6 + 7^3 - 4^4 - 1^0}{8^1 + 7^1 + 4^2 - 1^0} & 8757 := \frac{8^1 + 7^5 + 5^9 + 7^7}{8^1 - 7^1 - 5^2 + 7^3} & 8776 := \frac{8^3 - 7^1 + 7^7 - 6^7}{8^1 - 7^0 + 7^2 + 6^1} \\
 8742 := \frac{8^1 + 7^2 + 4^0 + 2^{17}}{8^1 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 2^1} & 8758 := \frac{8^3 - 7^5 - 5^4 + 8^6}{8^1 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 8^1} & 8777 := \frac{8^0 - 7^5 - 7^5 + 7^7}{-8^0 - 7^1 + 7^2 + 7^2} \\
 8742 := \frac{8^1 + 7^2 + 4^0 + 2^{17}}{8^1 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 2^1} & 8759 := \frac{-8^5 + 7^0 - 5^1 + 9^5}{-8^1 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 9^1} & 8778 := \frac{-8^3 - 7^6 - 7^6 + 8^6}{8^0 + 7^0 - 7^1 + 8^1} \\
 8743 := \frac{8^5 + 7^0 + 4^2 + 3^7}{8^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 3^0} & 8762 := \frac{8^6 - 7^5 + 6^0 - 2^1}{8^0 + 7^0 - 6^1 + 2^5} & 8779 := \frac{-8^5 + 7^1 + 7^2 + 9^5}{-8^1 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 9^1} \\
 8743 := \frac{8^5 + 7^0 + 4^2 + 3^7}{8^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 3^0} & 8763 := \frac{8^3 + 7^5 - 6^2 + 3^5}{-8^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 3^0} & 8782 := \frac{-8^0 - 7^4 + 8^{10} - 2^{13}}{8^1 + 7^6 + 8^3 + 2^{12}} \\
 8744 := \frac{8^0 + 7^9 + 4^2 - 4^3}{8^4 + 7^1 + 4^4 + 4^4} & 8764 := \frac{8^3 - 7^0 + 6^7 + 4^0}{8^1 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 4^2} & 8783 := \frac{-8^2 + 7^4 + 8^5 + 3^3}{8^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}
 \end{array}$$

$$8784 := \frac{-8^0 + 7^2 - 8^4 + 4^8}{8^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$8785 := \frac{8^1 + 7^{10} + 8^5 + 5^1}{8^1 + 7^1 + 8^5 - 5^4}$$

$$8789 := \frac{8^5 - 7^4 + 8^6 + 9^5}{-8^0 + 7^2 + 8^0 - 9^1}$$

$$8790 := \frac{8^5 + 7^4 - 9^1 + 0^1}{8^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 0^0}$$

$$8791 := \frac{-8^4 + 7^6 + 9^3 + 1^0}{8^1 + 7^1 - 9^0 - 1^0}$$

$$8792 := \frac{8^5 + 7^3 + 9^1 + 2^{11}}{8^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8792 := \frac{8^5 + 7^3 + 9^1 + 2^{11}}{8^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8793 := \frac{-8^4 + 7^6 + 9^3 + 3^3}{8^1 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 3^1}$$

$$8794 := \frac{8^5 + 7^4 - 9^1 + 4^2}{8^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8795 := \frac{-8^7 + 7^8 - 9^1 - 5^3}{8^2 + 7^3 + 9^1 + 5^0}$$

$$8796 := \frac{8^5 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 6^1}{8^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8796 := \frac{8^5 + 7^4 + 9^1 + 6^1}{8^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8797 := \frac{8^5 + 7^5 - 9^2 + 7^6}{8^1 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 7^0}$$

$$8798 := \frac{8^2 + 7^2 + 9^5 - 8^5}{8^0 + 7^0 + 9^1 - 8^1}$$

$$8799 := \frac{8^6 - 7^6 - 9^5 - 9^5}{-8^1 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 9^1}$$

$$8803 := \frac{-8^1 - 8^1 - 0^0 + 3^{15}}{8^4 + 8^4 - 0^0 - 3^8}$$

$$8819 := \frac{-8^5 + 8^6 - 1^0 - 9^2}{8^1 + 8^1 + 1^1 + 9^1}$$

$$8822 := \frac{-8^0 - 8^0 - 2^{14} + 2^{17}}{8^0 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 2^1}$$

$$8823 := \frac{-8^4 + 8^5 - 2^4 - 3^7}{-8^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$8824 := \frac{-8^2 + 8^4 + 2^{10} + 4^8}{8^0 + 8^0 + 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$8825 := \frac{8^1 + 8^4 + 2^{12} + 5^4}{-8^0 - 8^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$8826 := \frac{8^1 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 6^6}{8^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 6^1}$$

$$8826 := \frac{8^1 + 8^5 + 2^1 + 6^6}{8^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 6^1}$$

$$8827 := \frac{8^3 + 8^8 - 2^1 + 7^4}{8^1 - 8^3 + 2^2 + 7^4}$$

$$8829 := \frac{8^0 + 8^6 + 2^{10} + 9^6}{8^0 + 8^2 + 2^4 + 9^1}$$

$$8829 := \frac{8^0 + 8^6 + 2^{10} + 9^6}{8^0 + 8^2 + 2^4 + 9^1}$$

$$8830 := \frac{8^3 + 8^8 - 3^6 + 0^0}{-8^1 + 8^4 - 3^7 - 0^0}$$

$$8832 := \frac{8^0 - 8^3 + 3^{11} + 2^2}{8^0 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 2^3}$$

$$8833 := \frac{8^3 + 8^7 + 3^{10} - 3^{12}}{8^1 - 8^2 - 3^1 + 3^5}$$

$$8835 := \frac{8^2 - 8^3 + 3^{11} + 5^0}{8^1 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 5^0}$$

$$8836 := \frac{-8^0 - 8^4 + 3^{12} - 6^7}{-8^0 + 8^0 + 3^3 + 6^0}$$

$$8837 := \frac{-8^2 + 8^5 + 3^5 + 7^4}{8^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8839 := \frac{8^2 - 8^3 + 3^{11} + 9^2}{8^0 + 8^0 + 3^2 + 9^1}$$

$$8842 := \frac{8^3 - 8^5 + 4^1 + 2^{18}}{8^0 + 8^0 + 4^2 + 2^3}$$

$$8843 := \frac{-8^1 - 8^5 + 4^4 + 3^{10}}{-8^0 - 8^0 + 4^1 + 3^0}$$

$$8844 := \frac{8^4 + 8^7 - 4^1 + 4^8}{8^0 - 8^1 - 4^1 + 4^4}$$

$$8845 := \frac{-8^3 + 8^5 - 4^0 + 5^5}{8^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8846 := \frac{8^2 + 8^4 - 4^5 + 6^7}{-8^0 + 8^0 - 4^1 + 6^2}$$

$$8847 := \frac{8^2 - 8^6 + 4^{10} - 7^5}{8^1 + 8^1 + 4^3 + 7^1}$$

$$8848 := \frac{8^3 + 8^4 + 4^7 + 8^6}{-8^1 - 8^1 - 4^2 + 8^2}$$

$$8849 := \frac{8^3 - 8^4 + 4^8 - 9^1}{8^0 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$8852 := \frac{8^0 + 8^6 - 5^4 + 2^{20}}{-8^0 + 8^1 + 5^3 + 2^4}$$

$$8853 := \frac{8^8 + 8^8 + 5^4 - 3^7}{-8^2 + 8^4 + 5^0 - 3^5}$$

$$8855 := \frac{-8^2 - 8^4 - 5^5 + 5^7}{8^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 5^1}$$

$$8857 := \frac{-8^2 + 8^4 - 5^5 + 7^5}{-8^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$8859 := \frac{8^6 + 8^6 + 5^7 - 9^0}{8^1 + 8^2 - 5^1 + 9^0}$$

$$8862 := \frac{-8^2 - 8^6 + 6^7 - 2^2}{-8^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8864 := \frac{8^3 + 8^3 + 6^5 + 4^3}{-8^0 - 8^0 - 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$8865 := \frac{8^3 + 8^7 + 6^3 + 5^5}{8^1 + 8^1 + 6^3 + 5^1}$$

$$8865 := \frac{8^3 + 8^7 + 6^3 + 5^5}{8^1 + 8^1 + 6^3 + 5^1}$$

$$8867 := \frac{8^2 + 8^6 + 6^8 + 7^2}{8^0 + 8^0 + 6^3 + 7^0}$$

$$8867 := \frac{8^2 + 8^6 + 6^8 + 7^2}{8^0 + 8^0 + 6^3 + 7^0}$$

$$8868 := \frac{8^1 - 8^2 + 6^7 - 8^6}{-8^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$8869 := \frac{-8^1 - 8^4 + 6^8 + 9^3}{8^1 + 8^2 + 6^2 + 9^2}$$

$$8870 := \frac{-8^4 + 8^8 + 7^2 + 0^0}{8^0 - 8^3 + 7^4 + 0^0}$$

$$8872 := \frac{-8^0 + 8^7 + 7^8 + 2^{14}}{8^0 + 8^3 + 7^3 + 2^5}$$

$$8873 := \frac{8^4 + 8^6 - 7^2 - 3^0}{8^0 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 3^3}$$

$$8875 := \frac{-8^2 - 8^3 - 7^2 + 5^9}{8^0 + 8^0 + 7^3 - 5^3}$$

$$8876 := \frac{-8^0 + 8^4 + 7^0 + 6^7}{-8^1 - 8^1 + 7^2 - 6^0}$$

$$8879 := \frac{8^4 + 8^6 + 7^2 + 9^2}{-8^0 - 8^0 - 7^2 + 9^2}$$

$$8887 := \frac{-8^1 - 8^3 - 8^5 + 7^9}{-8^2 + 8^3 + 8^4 - 7^1}$$

$$8893 := \frac{-8^1 - 8^1 + 9^3 + 3^{11}}{8^0 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 3^2}$$

$$8896 := \frac{-8^0 - 8^6 + 9^0 + 6^7}{-8^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8897 := \frac{-8^0 - 8^2 + 9^4 + 7^4}{8^0 - 8^1 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$8899 := \frac{8^5 + 8^5 + 9^0 + 9^5}{8^1 + 8^1 - 9^0 - 9^0}$$

$$8902 := \frac{8^7 + 9^4 - 0^0 + 2^{15}}{-8^1 - 9^1 + 0^0 + 2^8}$$

$$8903 := \frac{-8^6 - 9^5 - 0^0 + 3^{13}}{8^2 - 9^0 - 0^0 + 3^4}$$

$$8904 := \frac{-8^3 - 9^1 + 0^0 + 4^{11}}{-8^0 + 9^3 - 0^0 - 4^4}$$

$$8906 := \frac{8^5 + 9^3 + 0^0 + 6^6}{8^0 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 6^1}$$

$$8906 := \frac{8^5 + 9^3 + 0^0 + 6^6}{8^0 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 6^1}$$

$$8912 := \frac{-8^1 + 9^3 - 1^0 + 2^{13}}{-8^0 - 9^0 + 1^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8916 := \frac{8^6 + 9^5 - 1^0 - 6^3}{8^1 - 9^1 + 1^0 + 6^2}$$

$$8917 := \frac{8^8 + 9^2 - 1^0 - 7^8}{8^3 + 9^3 + 1^0 - 7^1}$$

$$8920 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^3 + 2^{13} + 0^1}{-8^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 0^1}$$

$$8921 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^3 + 2^{13} + 1^0}{-8^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 1^0}$$

$$8922 := \frac{8^0 + 9^3 + 2^{12} + 2^{12}}{-8^0 - 9^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$8923 := \frac{8^1 + 9^3 + 2^{15} + 3^7}{8^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8923 := \frac{8^1 + 9^3 + 2^{15} + 3^7}{8^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$8924 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^3 + 2^{13} + 4^1}{-8^0 - 9^0 - 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$8925 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^3 + 2^{13} + 5^1}{-8^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$8926 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^3 + 2^{13} + 6^1}{-8^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$8927 := \frac{8^3 + 9^4 + 2^8 + 7^6}{8^1 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$8927 := \frac{8^3 + 9^4 + 2^8 + 7^6}{8^1 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$8928 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^3 + 2^{13} + 8^1}{-8^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$8929 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^1 + 2^{13} + 9^3}{-8^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$8932 := \frac{8^5 + 9^6 + 3^{13} + 2^{16}}{8^0 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 2^2}$$

$$8932 := \frac{8^5 + 9^6 + 3^{13} + 2^{16}}{8^0 + 9^0 + 3^5 + 2^2}$$

$$8933 := \frac{8^2 + 9^2 + 3^{12} + 3^{12}}{8^1 + 9^2 + 3^1 + 3^3}$$

$$8933 := \frac{8^2 + 9^2 + 3^{12} + 3^{12}}{8^1 + 9^2 + 3^1 + 3^3}$$

$$8934 := \frac{8^3 + 9^3 + 3^5 + 4^7}{-8^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8935 := \frac{-8^2 + 9^4 + 3^9 + 5^4}{8^1 - 9^0 + 3^0 - 5^1}$$

$$8936 := \frac{8^3 - 9^2 + 3^6 + 6^5}{-8^0 - 9^0 - 3^1 + 6^1}$$

$$8937 := \frac{-8^5 + 9^2 + 3^{11} - 7^6}{8^1 + 9^0 + 3^0 - 7^1}$$

$$8938 := \frac{8^1 + 9^3 + 3^{13} - 8^4}{8^1 + 9^2 + 3^4 + 8^1}$$

$$8939 := \frac{-8^7 - 9^0 - 3^2 + 9^8}{8^4 - 9^0 - 3^5 + 9^3}$$

$$8942 := \frac{8^0 - 9^5 - 4^4 + 2^{19}}{8^0 - 9^1 - 4^1 + 2^6}$$

$$8943 := \frac{8^3 + 9^5 + 4^9 + 3^5}{8^1 + 9^1 + 4^2 + 3^1}$$

$$8943 := \frac{8^3 + 9^5 + 4^9 + 3^5}{8^1 + 9^1 + 4^2 + 3^1}$$

$$8944 := \frac{8^5 + 9^2 - 4^0 + 4^8}{8^1 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8945 := \frac{8^5 + 9^8 + 4^{10} + 5^7}{8^2 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 5^5}$$

$$8945 := \frac{8^5 + 9^8 + 4^{10} + 5^7}{8^2 + 9^3 + 4^5 + 5^5}$$

$$8946 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^6 + 4^9 + 6^7}{-8^0 + 9^2 + 4^1 + 6^2}$$

$$8947 := \frac{8^9 + 9^6 + 4^{12} + 7^1}{8^2 + 9^0 + 4^3 + 7^5}$$

$$8947 := \frac{8^9 + 9^6 + 4^{12} + 7^1}{8^2 + 9^0 + 4^3 + 7^5}$$

$$8948 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^4 + 4^8 - 8^3}{-8^0 + 9^0 + 4^2 - 8^1}$$

$$8952 := \frac{8^7 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 2^1}{8^0 + 9^2 + 5^2 + 2^7}$$

$$8952 := \frac{8^7 + 9^4 + 5^1 + 2^1}{8^0 + 9^2 + 5^2 + 2^7}$$

$$8953 := \frac{8^2 + 9^5 + 5^9 + 3^7}{8^2 + 9^1 + 5^3 + 3^3}$$

$$8953 := \frac{8^2 + 9^5 + 5^9 + 3^7}{8^2 + 9^1 + 5^3 + 3^3}$$

$$8954 := \frac{8^5 - 9^2 + 5^5 + 4^1}{8^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$8955 := \frac{8^3 + 9^5 - 5^0 + 5^5}{8^1 - 9^0 - 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$8956 := \frac{8^5 - 9^4 + 5^4 + 6^2}{-8^0 - 9^0 - 5^0 + 6^1}$$

$$8957 := \frac{8^6 + 9^1 + 5^0 - 7^4}{8^1 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 7^1}$$

$$8958 := \frac{-8^5 - 9^5 - 5^3 + 8^6}{8^0 + 9^1 + 5^0 + 8^1}$$

$$8960 := \frac{-8^4 + 9^6 + 6^4 - 0^0}{8^2 + 9^0 - 6^1 + 0^1}$$

$$8962 := \frac{8^8 + 9^4 + 6^0 + 2^{11}}{8^2 + 9^0 + 6^4 + 2^9}$$

$$8962 := \frac{8^8 + 9^4 + 6^0 + 2^{11}}{8^2 + 9^0 + 6^4 + 2^9}$$

$$8963 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^4 + 6^3 + 3^7}{-8^0 - 9^0 + 6^1 - 3^1}$$

$$8964 := \frac{-8^3 + 9^6 - 6^7 - 4^0}{-8^0 + 9^0 - 6^2 + 4^3}$$

$$8965 := \frac{8^5 + 9^6 + 6^6 + 5^9}{8^2 + 9^0 + 6^3 + 5^1}$$

$$8965 := \frac{8^5 + 9^6 + 6^6 + 5^9}{8^2 + 9^0 + 6^3 + 5^1}$$

$$8966 := \frac{-8^4 + 9^7 - 6^0 + 6^1}{8^3 + 9^1 + 6^1 + 6^1}$$

$$8967 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^4 + 6^1 + 7^4}{-8^0 + 9^0 - 6^1 + 7^1}$$

$$8968 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^6 - 6^6 - 8^3}{8^0 + 9^1 + 6^2 + 8^1}$$

$$8969 := \frac{8^3 - 9^0 + 6^7 + 9^4}{8^1 + 9^1 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$8970 := \frac{8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 0^1}{-8^0 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 0^1}$$

$$8971 := \frac{8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 1^0}{-8^1 + 9^0 + 7^1 + 1^0}$$

$$8972 := \frac{8^5 + 9^3 + 7^3 + 2^{11}}{8^0 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$8973 := \frac{8^{10} + 9^0 + 7^1 + 3^{16}}{8^1 + 9^4 + 7^6 + 3^5}$$

$$8974 := \frac{8^2 + 9^5 + 7^6 + 4^8}{8^0 + 9^1 + 7^0 + 4^2}$$

$$8975 := \frac{8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 5^1}{8^1 - 9^0 - 7^0 - 5^1}$$

$$8976 := \frac{8^5 + 9^3 + 7^4 + 6^1}{8^0 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$8977 := \frac{8^1 + 9^4 + 7^1 + 7^4}{-8^1 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 7^1}$$

$$8978 := \frac{8^1 + 9^4 + 7^4 + 8^1}{-8^0 + 9^0 - 7^1 + 8^1}$$

$$8979 := \frac{8^1 + 9^1 + 7^4 + 9^4}{-8^1 - 9^0 + 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$8982 := \frac{8^0 - 9^6 + 8^8 + 2^{16}}{-8^0 + 9^3 + 8^2 + 2^{10}}$$

$$8983 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^2 + 8^6 - 3^9}{8^0 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 3^2}$$

$$8984 := \frac{-8^0 + 9^5 + 8^4 - 4^4}{8^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$8987 := \frac{-8^2 - 9^4 + 8^5 + 7^6}{-8^0 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 7^1}$$

$$8992 := \frac{8^6 + 9^0 - 9^4 + 2^{17}}{8^0 + 9^0 + 9^1 + 2^5}$$

$$8994 := \frac{-8^2 - 9^2 + 9^4 + 4^8}{-8^0 - 9^0 + 9^1 + 4^0}$$

$$8995 := \frac{-8^5 + 9^3 + 9^5 - 5^2}{8^1 - 9^0 + 9^0 - 5^1}$$

$$8997 := \frac{-8^4 + 9^1 - 9^3 + 7^7}{8^1 + 9^0 + 9^2 + 7^0}$$

$$9012 := \frac{9^4 + 0^1 - 1^0 + 2^{16}}{-9^0 + 0^1 + 1^0 + 2^3}$$

$$9018 := \frac{9^6 + 0^1 - 1^0 + 8^6}{9^2 + 0^1 - 1^0 + 8^1}$$

$$9021 := \frac{9^5 + 0^0 + 2^{12} + 1^0}{9^0 + 0^0 + 2^2 + 1^0}$$

$$9021 := \frac{9^5 + 0^0 + 2^{12} + 1^0}{9^0 + 0^0 + 2^2 + 1^0}$$

$$9022 := \frac{9^5 + 0^0 + 2^3 + 2^{12}}{9^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 2^2}$$

$$9022 := \frac{9^5 + 0^0 + 2^3 + 2^{12}}{9^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 2^2}$$

$$9024 := \frac{9^7 - 0^0 + 2^3 - 4^4}{9^0 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^2}$$

$$9026 := \frac{9^5 + 0^0 + 2^{12} + 6^2}{9^0 + 0^0 + 2^2 + 6^0}$$

$$9026 := \frac{9^5 + 0^0 + 2^{12} + 6^2}{9^0 + 0^0 + 2^2 + 6^0}$$

$$9027 := \frac{9^4 + 0^0 + 2^6 + 7^4}{-9^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$9028 := \frac{-9^3 + 0^0 + 2^{19} + 8^2}{-9^0 - 0^0 - 2^2 + 8^2}$$

$$9032 := \frac{-9^4 + 0^1 + 3^{12} - 2^{10}}{-9^0 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 2^5}$$

$$9036 := \frac{9^5 + 0^1 + 3^{11} + 6^5}{-9^0 + 0^0 - 3^2 + 6^2}$$

$$9042 := \frac{9^1 + 0^0 + 4^3 + 2^{18}}{9^1 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 2^4}$$

$$9042 := \frac{9^1 + 0^0 + 4^3 + 2^{18}}{9^1 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 2^4}$$

$$9044 := \frac{9^4 - 0^0 + 4^4 + 4^8}{-9^0 + 0^0 + 4^1 + 4^1}$$

$$9045 := \frac{9^4 + 0^1 - 4^6 + 5^6}{-9^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9047 := \frac{-9^1 - 0^0 - 4^4 + 7^7}{9^2 - 0^0 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$9048 := \frac{9^7 - 0^0 - 4^8 + 8^5}{9^1 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 8^3}$$

$$9052 := \frac{9^3 + 0^1 - 5^0 + 2^{19}}{9^0 + 0^1 + 5^2 + 2^5}$$

$$9055 := \frac{9^6 - 0^0 - 5^5 - 5^5}{9^1 - 0^0 + 5^2 + 5^2}$$

$$9057 := \frac{-9^4 + 0^1 + 5^6 - 7^1}{-9^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$9062 := \frac{9^3 + 0^0 + 6^7 + 2^8}{9^1 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 2^4}$$

$$9062 := \frac{9^3 + 0^0 + 6^7 + 2^8}{9^1 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 2^4}$$

$$9065 := \frac{-9^4 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 5^6}{9^0 + 0^0 - 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$9067 := \frac{9^8 + 0^0 - 6^3 - 7^9}{-9^1 - 0^0 - 6^2 + 7^3}$$

$$9068 := \frac{9^7 - 0^0 - 6^2 - 8^4}{9^1 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 8^3}$$

$$9069 := \frac{9^7 + 0^1 + 6^3 + 9^8}{9^1 + 0^1 - 6^4 + 9^4}$$

$$9072 := \frac{9^6 + 0^1 - 7^6 - 2^{15}}{9^1 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 2^5}$$

$$9073 := \frac{9^4 + 0^0 + 7^7 + 3^{10}}{9^1 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 3^4}$$

$$9073 := \frac{9^4 + 0^0 + 7^7 + 3^{10}}{9^1 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 3^4}$$

$$9077 := \frac{9^1 + 0^1 + 7^3 + 7^6}{-9^0 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 7^1}$$

$$9083 := \frac{9^7 - 0^0 - 8^3 - 3^{13}}{-9^2 + 0^0 + 8^3 - 3^4}$$

$$9092 := \frac{-9^1 + 0^1 + 9^6 - 2^{12}}{9^1 + 0^1 + 9^2 - 2^5}$$

$$9094 := \frac{-9^3 + 0^1 - 9^4 + 4^7}{-9^0 - 0^0 - 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9096 := \frac{9^5 + 0^1 - 9^7 + 6^{11}}{-9^3 + 0^1 - 9^4 + 6^6}$$

$$9122 := \frac{9^4 + 1^0 + 2^9 + 2^{11}}{-9^0 - 1^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$9123 := \frac{9^4 - 1^0 + 2^8 + 3^{12}}{-9^0 + 1^0 + 2^5 + 3^3}$$

$$9124 := \frac{9^7 - 1^0 - 2^7 + 4^7}{9^1 + 1^0 + 2^9 + 4^1}$$

$$9125 := \frac{9^6 + 1^0 - 2^{13} - 5^5}{-9^0 + 1^0 + 2^5 + 5^2}$$

$$9126 := \frac{-9^0 - 1^0 - 2^{10} + 6^6}{9^0 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$9127 := \frac{-9^8 - 1^0 + 2^6 + 7^{10}}{9^5 + 1^0 - 2^{15} - 7^2}$$

$$9137 := \frac{9^6 - 1^0 - 3^3 + 7^5}{9^0 + 1^0 + 3^2 + 7^2}$$

$$9144 := \frac{9^6 - 1^0 - 4^3 - 4^5}{-9^0 - 1^0 - 4^1 + 4^3}$$

$$9147 := \frac{9^5 + 1^0 + 4^{11} + 7^0}{9^3 - 1^0 - 4^4 - 7^1}$$

$$9148 := \frac{9^5 - 1^0 - 4^3 - 8^4}{9^0 + 1^0 - 4^1 + 8^1}$$

$$9152 := \frac{9^6 - 1^0 - 5^4 + 2^0}{9^2 + 1^0 - 5^2 + 2^0}$$

$$9157 := \frac{9^5 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 7^8}{9^1 + 1^0 + 5^4 + 7^0}$$

$$9157 := \frac{9^5 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 7^8}{9^1 + 1^0 + 5^4 + 7^0}$$

$$9162 := \frac{-9^1 - 1^0 + 6^7 + 2^{12}}{-9^0 - 1^0 + 6^0 + 2^5}$$

$$9164 := \frac{-9^0 + 1^0 + 6^5 + 4^8}{-9^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 + 4^1}$$

$$9168 := \frac{-9^4 + 1^0 + 6^4 + 8^5}{-9^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 - 8^0}$$

$$9169 := \frac{-9^2 - 1^0 + 6^6 - 9^3}{-9^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 + 9^0}$$

$$9179 := \frac{-9^4 + 1^0 + 7^6 + 9^6}{-9^1 - 1^0 - 7^0 + 9^2}$$

$$9182 := \frac{9^5 + 1^0 + 8^5 + 2^1}{-9^0 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 2^1}$$

$$9186 := \frac{9^6 + 1^0 - 8^2 - 6^5}{-9^1 + 1^0 + 8^2 + 6^0}$$

$$9188 := \frac{9^5 - 1^0 + 8^2 + 8^5}{9^1 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9202 := \frac{9^6 + 2^{11} + 0^0 - 2^{19}}{-9^0 - 2^0 + 0^0 + 2^1}$$

$$9203 := \frac{9^5 + 2^{12} - 0^0 + 3^9}{9^0 + 2^2 + 0^0 + 3^1}$$

$$9205 := \frac{9^2 + 2^{18} + 0^1 - 5^7}{-9^0 - 2^2 + 0^1 + 5^2}$$

$$9206 := \frac{9^5 + 2^{12} + 0^0 + 6^4}{9^0 + 2^2 + 0^0 + 6^0}$$

$$9206 := \frac{9^5 + 2^{12} + 0^0 + 6^4}{9^0 + 2^2 + 0^0 + 6^0}$$

$$9209 := \frac{-9^4 + 2^5 + 0^0 + 9^6}{9^0 + 2^6 + 0^0 - 9^1}$$

$$9212 := \frac{-9^1 + 2^{11} + 1^0 + 2^{14}}{-9^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 2^0}$$

$$9213 := \frac{-9^1 - 2^{17} - 1^0 + 3^{11}}{9^0 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9214 := \frac{-9^0 + 2^{13} - 1^0 + 4^5}{-9^0 - 2^0 - 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9216 := \frac{9^4 + 2^{12} - 1^0 + 6^5}{-9^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$9217 := \frac{9^4 + 2^8 - 1^0 + 7^4}{9^0 - 2^1 + 1^0 + 7^0}$$

$$9218 := \frac{9^1 + 2^{12} - 1^0 + 8^5}{9^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9220 := \frac{9^1 + 2^{11} + 2^{14} - 0^0}{-9^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 0^0}$$

$$9221 := \frac{9^1 + 2^{11} + 2^{14} + 1^0}{-9^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 1^0}$$

$$9223 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{15} + 3^3}{9^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9223 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{15} + 3^3}{9^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9224 := \frac{9^1 - 2^0 + 2^{13} + 4^5}{-9^0 - 2^0 - 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9225 := \frac{9^7 + 2^{16} + 2^{18} + 5^0}{9^0 + 2^4 + 2^9 + 5^2}$$

$$9225 := \frac{9^7 + 2^{16} + 2^{18} + 5^0}{9^0 + 2^4 + 2^9 + 5^2}$$

$$9226 := \frac{9^1 + 2^{10} + 2^{13} + 6^0}{-9^0 - 2^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$9227 := \frac{9^2 + 2^{13} + 2^{16} + 7^1}{9^0 + 2^1 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$9227 := \frac{9^2 + 2^{13} + 2^{16} + 7^1}{9^0 + 2^1 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$9228 := \frac{-9^3 + 2^0 + 2^{20} - 8^5}{-9^0 - 2^4 + 2^7 - 8^0}$$

$$9229 := \frac{9^3 - 2^8 + 2^{15} + 9^5}{9^0 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 9^0}$$

$$9231 := \frac{9^2 - 2^{17} + 3^{11} - 1^0}{9^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 1^0}$$

$$9232 := \frac{9^6 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 2^{17}}{9^0 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 2^6}$$

$$9232 := \frac{9^6 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 2^{17}}{9^0 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 2^6}$$

$$9233 := \frac{9^4 + 2^{15} + 3^8 + 3^{14}}{9^0 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 3^2}$$

$$9233 := \frac{9^4 + 2^{15} + 3^8 + 3^{14}}{9^0 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 3^2}$$

$$9234 := \frac{9^6 + 2^3 + 3^3 + 4^6}{9^0 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^2}$$

$$9234 := \frac{9^6 + 2^3 + 3^3 + 4^6}{9^0 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^2}$$

$$9235 := \frac{9^3 + 2^{18} + 3^7 + 5^8}{9^0 + 2^6 + 3^0 + 5^1}$$

$$9235 := \frac{9^3 + 2^{18} + 3^7 + 5^8}{9^0 + 2^6 + 3^0 + 5^1}$$

$$9236 := \frac{9^7 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 6^2}{9^0 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 6^1}$$

$$9237 := \frac{9^5 + 2^1 + 3^{13} + 7^2}{9^0 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 7^2}$$

$$9238 := \frac{9^4 + 2^{13} + 3^5 + 8^6}{9^0 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 8^0}$$

$$9238 := \frac{9^4 + 2^{13} + 3^5 + 8^6}{9^0 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 8^0}$$

$$9239 := \frac{-9^5 + 2^1 - 3^9 + 9^6}{9^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1}$$

$$9240 := \frac{-9^3 - 2^7 + 4^8 + 0^0}{9^0 + 2^0 + 4^1 + 0^0}$$

$$9242 := \frac{9^3 - 2^0 - 4^6 + 2^{18}}{9^1 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 2^1}$$

$$9243 := \frac{9^2 + 2^{15} + 4^6 + 3^3}{9^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9243 := \frac{9^2 + 2^{15} + 4^6 + 3^3}{9^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9244 := \frac{9^5 + 2^9 - 4^0 - 4^6}{-9^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 + 4^1}$$

$$9245 := \frac{9^3 + 2^{13} + 4^7 + 5^9}{9^1 + 2^4 + 4^3 + 5^3}$$

$$9245 := \frac{9^3 + 2^{13} + 4^7 + 5^9}{9^1 + 2^4 + 4^3 + 5^3}$$

$$9246 := \frac{9^4 + 2^7 + 4^0 + 6^7}{9^0 + 2^3 + 4^2 + 6^1}$$

$$9246 := \frac{9^4 + 2^7 + 4^0 + 6^7}{9^0 + 2^3 + 4^2 + 6^1}$$

$$9247 := \frac{9^1 + 2^{17} + 4^3 + 7^5}{9^0 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$9247 := \frac{9^1 + 2^{17} + 4^3 + 7^5}{9^0 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$9248 := \frac{9^4 - 2^0 + 4^9 - 8^3}{9^0 + 2^2 + 4^2 + 8^1}$$

$$9250 := \frac{-9^1 + 2^{14} + 5^8 + 0^1}{-9^2 - 2^0 + 5^3 + 0^0}$$

$$9251 := \frac{9^6 - 2^4 - 5^7 - 1^0}{9^1 + 2^4 + 5^2 - 1^0}$$

$$9252 := \frac{9^6 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 2^{11}}{9^0 + 2^4 + 5^2 + 2^4}$$

$$9252 := \frac{9^6 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 2^{11}}{9^0 + 2^4 + 5^2 + 2^4}$$

$$9253 := \frac{9^4 - 2^{14} + 5^7 - 3^{10}}{9^0 - 2^1 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9254 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{15} + 5^6 + 4^7}{9^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9254 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{15} + 5^6 + 4^7}{9^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9255 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{18} + 5^5 + 5^5}{9^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 5^2}$$

$$9255 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{18} + 5^5 + 5^5}{9^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 5^2}$$

$$9256 := \frac{9^7 + 2^1 + 5^3 + 6^7}{9^1 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 6^0}$$

$$9256 := \frac{9^7 + 2^1 + 5^3 + 6^7}{9^1 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 6^0}$$

$$9257 := \frac{9^6 + 2^{15} + 5^3 + 7^3}{9^1 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 7^2}$$

$$9257 := \frac{9^6 + 2^{15} + 5^3 + 7^3}{9^1 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 7^2}$$

$$9258 := \frac{-9^3 + 2^{15} - 5^0 + 8^5}{9^0 + 2^2 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9259 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{16} + 5^1 - 9^3}{9^0 + 2^2 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$9260 := \frac{9^3 - 2^{18} + 6^7 - 0^0}{-9^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 0^0}$$

$$9261 := \frac{9^3 - 2^{18} + 6^7 + 1^0}{-9^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$9262 := \frac{9^2 + 2^0 + 6^5 + 2^{17}}{9^0 + 2^2 + 6^1 + 2^2}$$

$$9262 := \frac{9^2 + 2^0 + 6^5 + 2^{17}}{9^0 + 2^2 + 6^1 + 2^2}$$

$$9263 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{13} + 6^6 + 3^6}{9^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$$

$$9263 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{13} + 6^6 + 3^6}{9^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$$

$$9264 := \frac{-9^2 + 2^0 + 6^6 - 4^4}{9^0 + 2^1 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$9265 := \frac{9^6 + 2^{15} + 6^6 + 5^4}{9^0 + 2^2 + 6^2 + 5^2}$$

$$9265 := \frac{9^6 + 2^{15} + 6^6 + 5^4}{9^0 + 2^2 + 6^2 + 5^2}$$

$$9267 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{20} + 6^6 + 7^5}{9^0 + 2^6 + 6^1 + 7^2}$$

$$9267 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{20} + 6^6 + 7^5}{9^0 + 2^6 + 6^1 + 7^2}$$

$$9269 := \frac{-9^0 + 2^{17} - 6^4 - 9^1}{9^0 - 2^1 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$9271 := \frac{9^4 + 2^{19} - 7^4 - 1^0}{-9^0 + 2^3 + 7^2 + 1^0}$$

$$9272 := \frac{9^1 + 2^{10} + 7^7 + 2^{16}}{9^1 + 2^4 + 7^1 + 2^6}$$

$$9272 := \frac{9^1 + 2^{10} + 7^7 + 2^{16}}{9^1 + 2^4 + 7^1 + 2^6}$$

$$9273 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{10} + 7^7 + 3^6}{9^1 + 2^2 + 7^2 + 3^3}$$

$$9273 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{10} + 7^7 + 3^6}{9^1 + 2^2 + 7^2 + 3^3}$$

$$9274 := \frac{9^6 + 2^{12} + 7^5 + 4^6}{9^1 + 2^0 + 7^2 + 4^0}$$

$$9274 := \frac{9^6 + 2^{12} + 7^5 + 4^6}{9^1 + 2^0 + 7^2 + 4^0}$$

$$9275 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{13} + 7^1 + 5^8}{9^0 + 2^4 + 7^0 + 5^2}$$

$$9275 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{13} + 7^1 + 5^8}{9^0 + 2^4 + 7^0 + 5^2}$$

$$9276 := \frac{9^2 + 2^3 + 7^5 + 6^7}{9^1 + 2^4 + 7^0 + 6^1}$$

$$9276 := \frac{9^2 + 2^3 + 7^5 + 6^7}{9^1 + 2^4 + 7^0 + 6^1}$$

$$9277 := \frac{9^7 - 2^9 - 7^4 - 7^4}{9^0 + 2^9 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$9278 := \frac{9^0 - 2^{19} + 7^7 - 8^6}{9^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9279 := \frac{9^5 + 2^7 + 7^4 + 9^5}{9^0 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$9279 := \frac{9^5 + 2^7 + 7^4 + 9^5}{9^0 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$9280 := \frac{-9^0 + 2^{20} + 8^2 + 0^0}{9^2 + 2^5 - 8^0 + 0^0}$$

$$9283 := \frac{9^3 + 2^4 - 8^4 + 3^{10}}{9^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 3^1}$$

$$9284 := \frac{9^5 - 2^0 + 8^5 + 4^5}{9^0 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9285 := \frac{-9^4 - 2^{15} + 8^6 + 5^2}{9^1 + 2^1 + 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$9286 := \frac{9^6 - 2^1 - 8^6 - 6^0}{-9^0 + 2^1 - 8^1 + 6^2}$$

$$9287 := \frac{9^2 + 2^{13} + 8^4 + 7^6}{9^0 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$9287 := \frac{9^2 + 2^{13} + 8^4 + 7^6}{9^0 + 2^2 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$9288 := \frac{-9^1 + 2^{16} + 8^0 - 8^3}{9^0 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9289 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{19} - 8^4 - 9^1}{-9^0 + 2^1 + 8^2 - 9^1}$$

$$9292 := \frac{9^0 - 2^8 - 9^3 + 2^{17}}{9^0 + 2^1 + 9^1 + 2^1}$$

$$9293 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{16} - 9^3 + 3^5}{9^0 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 3^1}$$

$$9294 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{12} + 9^5 + 4^9}{9^0 + 2^5 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$9294 := \frac{9^0 + 2^{12} + 9^5 + 4^9}{9^0 + 2^5 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$9295 := \frac{9^4 - 2^{13} + 9^6 + 5^1}{-9^0 + 2^1 + 9^2 - 5^2}$$

$$9296 := \frac{-9^0 - 2^8 + 9^2 + 6^6}{9^0 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$9297 := \frac{9^1 - 2^6 + 9^5 + 7^6}{9^0 + 2^1 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$9298 := \frac{9^2 - 2^{10} + 9^6 - 8^3}{9^0 + 2^0 - 9^1 + 8^2}$$

$$9306 := \frac{9^6 - 3^5 + 0^1 - 6^7}{-9^0 - 3^2 + 0^0 + 6^2}$$

$$9321 := \frac{-9^2 + 3^{11} + 2^5 + 1^0}{9^0 + 3^0 + 2^4 + 1^0}$$

$$9322 := \frac{9^0 + 3^0 + 2^{13} + 2^{18}}{9^1 + 3^1 + 2^0 + 2^4}$$

$$9322 := \frac{9^0 + 3^0 + 2^{13} + 2^{18}}{9^1 + 3^1 + 2^0 + 2^4}$$

$$9323 := \frac{-9^0 - 3^0 - 2^3 + 3^{11}}{9^0 + 3^0 + 2^3 + 3^2}$$

$$9324 := \frac{9^0 + 3^{11} + 2^2 + 4^1}{9^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 4^2}$$

$$9325 := \frac{9^5 + 3^{10} + 2^1 + 5^5}{9^0 + 3^1 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$9325 := \frac{9^5 + 3^{10} + 2^1 + 5^5}{9^0 + 3^1 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$9326 := \frac{9^1 + 3^{11} + 2^1 + 6^2}{9^0 + 3^0 + 2^4 + 6^0}$$

$$9326 := \frac{9^1 + 3^{11} + 2^1 + 6^2}{9^0 + 3^0 + 2^4 + 6^0}$$

$$9327 := \frac{9^0 + 3^{11} + 2^4 + 7^2}{9^0 + 3^0 + 2^4 + 7^0}$$

$$9327 := \frac{9^0 + 3^{11} + 2^4 + 7^2}{9^0 + 3^0 + 2^4 + 7^0}$$

$$9328 := \frac{-9^1 + 3^{10} + 2^{10} - 8^4}{9^0 + 3^1 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9329 := \frac{-9^1 + 3^6 + 2^{11} + 9^4}{-9^0 - 3^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}$$

$$9332 := \frac{9^2 + 3^4 + 3^{11} - 2^0}{9^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 2^4}$$

$$9333 := \frac{-9^1 + 3^6 + 3^{11} + 3^{12}}{-9^0 - 3^0 - 3^1 + 3^4}$$

$$9335 := \frac{9^5 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 5^6}{9^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 5^1}$$

$$9335 := \frac{9^5 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 5^6}{9^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 5^1}$$

$$9337 := \frac{9^7 + 3^1 - 3^3 - 7^4}{9^3 - 3^1 + 3^7 - 7^4}$$

$$9338 := \frac{9^4 - 3^5 + 3^{10} - 8^0}{-9^0 - 3^0 + 3^0 + 8^1}$$

$$9340 := \frac{9^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 0^1}{-9^0 - 3^1 + 4^3 - 0^0}$$

$$9341 := \frac{9^6 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 1^0}{9^0 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 1^0}$$

$$9342 := \frac{9^1 + 3^9 + 4^8 + 2^{13}}{9^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 2^2}$$

$$9342 := \frac{9^1 + 3^9 + 4^8 + 2^{13}}{9^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 2^2}$$

$$9343 := \frac{-9^2 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 3^3}{9^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 3^0}$$

$$9344 := \frac{9^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 4^5}{9^0 - 3^2 + 4^0 + 4^3}$$

$$9345 := \frac{9^0 + 3^1 + 4^8 - 5^3}{9^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$9346 := \frac{9^{10} + 3^{11} + 4^{13} + 6^5}{9^5 + 3^{10} + 4^9 + 6^2}$$

$$9346 := \frac{9^{10} + 3^{11} + 4^{13} + 6^5}{9^5 + 3^{10} + 4^9 + 6^2}$$

$$9347 := \frac{9^4 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^3}{-9^0 - 3^0 + 4^1 - 7^0}$$

$$9348 := \frac{9^6 + 3^9 + 4^9 + 8^1}{9^0 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 8^0}$$

$$9348 := \frac{9^6 + 3^9 + 4^9 + 8^1}{9^0 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 8^0}$$

$$9349 := \frac{-9^1 - 3^1 + 4^8 - 9^2}{9^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$9352 := \frac{9^8 - 3^{11} - 5^1 - 2^0}{9^3 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 2^0}$$

$$9353 := \frac{-9^3 - 3^5 - 5^1 + 3^9}{-9^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9354 := \frac{9^1 + 3^{14} + 5^6 - 4^0}{9^1 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 4^4}$$

$$9355 := \frac{9^2 + 3^{10} + 5^3 - 5^5}{9^0 + 3^1 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9356 := \frac{-9^1 + 3^{11} + 5^4 + 6^0}{9^1 + 3^1 + 5^0 + 6^1}$$

$$9357 := \frac{-9^0 + 3^9 - 5^4 - 7^3}{-9^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$9358 := \frac{-9^3 + 3^9 + 5^{12} - 8^0}{9^1 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^5}$$

$$9359 := \frac{-9^2 + 3^9 + 5^9 - 9^6}{9^0 + 3^3 + 5^3 + 9^0}$$

$$9360 := \frac{9^3 + 3^{11} - 6^2 + 0^1}{9^1 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 0^0}$$

$$9362 := \frac{9^1 + 3^4 + 6^6 + 2^6}{9^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$9363 := \frac{9^6 + 3^3 + 6^2 + 3^7}{9^1 + 3^1 + 6^2 + 3^2}$$

$$9363 := \frac{9^6 + 3^3 + 6^2 + 3^7}{9^1 + 3^1 + 6^2 + 3^2}$$

$$9364 := \frac{9^5 + 3^7 + 6^3 + 4^6}{9^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9364 := \frac{9^5 + 3^7 + 6^3 + 4^6}{9^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9365 := \frac{9^6 + 3^{13} + 6^3 - 5^3}{9^0 + 3^2 + 6^3 + 5^0}$$

$$9366 := \frac{-9^3 + 3^9 - 6^1 - 6^3}{-9^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$9367 := \frac{-9^2 - 3^6 + 6^5 + 7^4}{-9^0 + 3^0 - 6^1 + 7^1}$$

$$9368 := \frac{-9^0 + 3^8 + 6^8 + 8^2}{-9^0 - 3^3 + 6^3 - 8^1}$$

$$9369 := \frac{9^6 + 3^{12} + 6^5 + 9^6}{9^2 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 9^2}$$

$$9369 := \frac{9^6 + 3^{12} + 6^5 + 9^6}{9^2 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 9^2}$$

$$9372 := \frac{9^4 + 3^{10} - 7^1 + 2^0}{9^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 2^2}$$

$$9373 := \frac{9^0 - 3^8 + 7^1 + 3^{12}}{9^0 + 3^1 + 7^2 + 3^1}$$

$$9374 := \frac{9^4 + 3^{10} + 7^1 + 4^0}{9^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9374 := \frac{9^4 + 3^{10} + 7^1 + 4^0}{9^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9375 := \frac{9^3 + 3^{11} + 7^{10} + 5^{11}}{9^0 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 5^6}$$

$$9375 := \frac{9^3 + 3^{11} + 7^{10} + 5^{11}}{9^0 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 5^6}$$

$$9376 := \frac{-9^3 + 3^{19} - 7^4 - 6^0}{9^4 - 3^5 + 7^6 - 6^1}$$

$$9377 := \frac{-9^3 + 3^{10} + 7^3 - 7^4}{9^0 + 3^1 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$9378 := \frac{-9^1 - 3^{13} + 7^9 - 8^0}{9^1 + 3^3 + 7^0 + 8^4}$$

$$9379 := \frac{9^0 - 3^8 + 7^3 + 9^6}{-9^0 - 3^0 + 7^2 + 9^1}$$

$$9381 := \frac{9^5 + 3^{12} + 8^3 + 1^0}{-9^0 - 3^0 + 8^2 + 1^0}$$

$$9382 := \frac{9^5 + 3^1 + 8^6 + 2^{20}}{9^0 + 3^2 + 8^1 + 2^7}$$

$$9382 := \frac{9^5 + 3^1 + 8^6 + 2^{20}}{9^0 + 3^2 + 8^1 + 2^7}$$

$$9383 := \frac{9^2 + 3^{12} + 8^4 + 3^{13}}{9^0 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 3^4}$$

$$9383 := \frac{9^2 + 3^{12} + 8^4 + 3^{13}}{9^0 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 3^4}$$

$$9384 := \frac{-9^2 + 3^8 - 8^4 + 4^7}{-9^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 4^0}$$

$$9385 := \frac{9^2 + 3^{13} + 8^0 + 5^9}{9^1 + 3^5 + 8^0 + 5^3}$$

$$9386 := \frac{9^5 + 3^{11} + 8^2 + 6^5}{9^1 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 6^1}$$

$$9386 := \frac{9^5 + 3^{11} + 8^2 + 6^5}{9^1 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 6^1}$$

$$9387 := \frac{9^2 + 3^8 + 8^7 + 7^9}{9^2 + 3^1 + 8^4 + 7^3}$$

$$9387 := \frac{9^2 + 3^8 + 8^7 + 7^9}{9^2 + 3^1 + 8^4 + 7^3}$$

$$9388 := \frac{-9^0 + 3^6 - 8^1 + 8^6}{9^1 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 8^1}$$

$$9389 := \frac{9^2 - 3^{11} + 8^4 + 9^7}{-9^1 - 3^1 + 8^3 - 9^1}$$

$$9393 := \frac{9^4 + 3^1 + 9^7 + 3^9}{-9^0 + 3^3 + 9^3 - 3^5}$$

$$9395 := \frac{9^3 - 3^5 + 9^5 + 5^6}{9^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 5^1}$$

$$9397 := \frac{-9^2 - 3^5 + 9^6 - 7^6}{9^0 + 3^3 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$9407 := \frac{9^4 + 4^{12} + 0^0 + 7^8}{-9^0 - 4^1 + 0^0 + 7^4}$$

$$9418 := \frac{9^6 + 4^3 - 1^0 - 8^4}{-9^0 + 4^3 + 1^0 - 8^1}$$

$$9420 := \frac{-9^4 + 4^7 + 2^{16} + 0^0}{9^0 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 0^0}$$

$$9421 := \frac{9^5 - 4^3 + 2^{14} - 1^0}{9^0 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 1^0}$$

$$9422 := \frac{9^7 - 4^{11} + 2^0 - 2^{15}}{9^1 + 4^2 + 2^1 + 2^5}$$

$$9423 := \frac{9^1 + 4^1 + 2^{17} + 3^9}{9^0 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 3^2}$$

$$9423 := \frac{9^1 + 4^1 + 2^{17} + 3^9}{9^0 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 3^2}$$

$$9424 := \frac{9^4 - 4^0 - 2^{12} + 4^7}{-9^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$9425 := \frac{9^4 + 4^6 + 2^{13} + 5^0}{-9^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9426 := \frac{9^3 + 4^0 - 2^8 + 6^6}{9^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$9427 := \frac{9^0 + 4^{13} + 2^{16} + 7^4}{9^4 + 4^1 + 2^9 + 7^2}$$

$$9427 := \frac{9^0 + 4^{13} + 2^{16} + 7^4}{9^4 + 4^1 + 2^9 + 7^2}$$

$$9428 := \frac{9^5 - 4^0 + 2^{14} - 8^1}{9^0 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 8^0}$$

$$9429 := \frac{9^7 + 4^2 + 2^{15} + 9^7}{9^0 + 4^4 + 2^5 + 9^3}$$

$$9429 := \frac{9^7 + 4^2 + 2^{15} + 9^7}{9^0 + 4^4 + 2^5 + 9^3}$$

$$9431 := \frac{9^3 + 4^{10} - 3^{10} - 1^0}{9^1 + 4^2 + 3^4 - 1^0}$$

$$9432 := \frac{9^3 + 4^1 + 3^5 + 2^{17}}{9^0 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 2^3}$$

$$9432 := \frac{9^3 + 4^1 + 3^5 + 2^{17}}{9^0 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 2^3}$$

$$9433 := \frac{9^1 + 4^8 + 3^5 + 3^5}{9^0 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9433 := \frac{9^1 + 4^8 + 3^5 + 3^5}{9^0 + 4^1 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9434 := \frac{9^3 + 4^2 - 3^5 + 4^8}{9^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9435 := \frac{-9^2 + 4^9 - 3^{11} - 5^0}{9^0 + 4^1 + 3^1 + 5^0}$$

$$9436 := \frac{9^2 + 4^3 + 3^{13} + 6^3}{9^2 + 4^0 + 3^4 + 6^1}$$

$$9436 := \frac{9^2 + 4^3 + 3^{13} + 6^3}{9^2 + 4^0 + 3^4 + 6^1}$$

$$9437 := \frac{-9^3 + 4^7 - 3^8 + 7^3}{-9^0 + 4^1 - 3^0 - 7^0}$$

$$9438 := \frac{9^2 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 8^5}{9^0 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 8^0}$$

$$9438 := \frac{9^2 + 4^6 + 3^9 + 8^5}{9^0 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 8^0}$$

$$9439 := \frac{-9^0 + 4^9 - 3^6 - 9^4}{9^0 + 4^2 + 3^0 + 9^1}$$

$$9442 := \frac{-9^0 - 4^0 + 4^{10} - 2^9}{-9^0 + 4^2 + 4^3 + 2^5}$$

$$9443 := \frac{-9^3 - 4^1 - 4^3 + 3^9}{-9^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9444 := \frac{-9^8 + 4^0 + 4^{11} + 4^{13}}{-9^2 + 4^0 - 4^5 + 4^6}$$

$$9445 := \frac{9^5 - 4^3 + 4^9 + 5^0}{9^0 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 5^2}$$

$$9446 := \frac{-9^7 - 4^0 + 4^{13} + 6^9}{9^2 + 4^3 - 4^4 + 6^5}$$

$$9447 := \frac{9^5 + 4^1 + 4^9 + 7^0}{9^0 + 4^2 + 4^2 + 7^0}$$

$$9447 := \frac{9^5 + 4^1 + 4^9 + 7^0}{9^0 + 4^2 + 4^2 + 7^0}$$

$$9448 := \frac{-9^5 - 4^7 + 4^{10} + 8^0}{-9^1 - 4^2 + 4^3 + 8^2}$$

$$9449 := \frac{9^1 + 4^3 + 4^9 + 9^5}{9^0 + 4^2 + 4^2 + 9^0}$$

$$9449 := \frac{9^1 + 4^3 + 4^9 + 9^5}{9^0 + 4^2 + 4^2 + 9^0}$$

$$9450 := \frac{-9^1 + 4^7 + 5^7 + 0^1}{9^0 + 4^1 + 5^1 + 0^1}$$

$$9452 := \frac{9^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 + 2^1}{9^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 2^2}$$

$$9452 := \frac{9^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 + 2^1}{9^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 2^2}$$

$$9453 := \frac{9^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 + 3^2}{9^0 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9453 := \frac{9^0 + 4^8 + 5^4 + 3^2}{9^0 + 4^1 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9454 := \frac{9^0 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 4^8}{9^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 4^1}$$

$9454 := \frac{9^0 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 4^8}{9^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 4^1}$	$9471 := \frac{9^7 - 4^3 - 7^2 - 1^0}{9^2 - 4^7 + 7^5 + 1^0}$	$9487 := \frac{9^5 + 4^7 + 8^3 - 7^2}{-9^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 7^1}$
$9455 := \frac{-9^1 - 4^8 - 5^5 + 5^7}{-9^0 + 4^1 - 5^0 - 5^0}$	$9472 := \frac{9^3 + 4^8 + 7^1 + 2^5}{9^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 2^2}$	$9488 := \frac{9^7 - 4^5 - 8^0 + 8^1}{-9^0 + 4^0 - 8^1 + 8^3}$
$9456 := \frac{9^5 + 4^7 - 5^0 + 6^3}{9^0 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 6^0}$	$9472 := \frac{9^3 + 4^8 + 7^1 + 2^5}{9^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 2^2}$	$9489 := \frac{-9^0 - 4^3 + 8^1 + 9^6}{-9^0 - 4^2 - 8^1 + 9^2}$
$9457 := \frac{9^4 + 4^0 + 5^8 + 7^1}{9^1 + 4^0 + 5^2 + 7^1}$	$9473 := \frac{-9^3 - 4^0 - 7^1 + 3^9}{-9^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$	$9490 := \frac{-9^0 - 4^0 + 9^6 + 0^0}{9^0 + 4^3 - 9^1 + 0^1}$
$9457 := \frac{9^4 + 4^0 + 5^8 + 7^1}{9^1 + 4^0 + 5^2 + 7^1}$	$9474 := \frac{9^3 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 4^8}{9^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 4^1}$	$9492 := \frac{-9^1 + 4^7 + 9^5 + 2^9}{9^0 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 2^1}$
$9458 := \frac{-9^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 8^3}{-9^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$	$9475 := \frac{9^4 + 4^6 - 7^5 + 5^6}{-9^0 + 4^1 - 7^0 - 5^0}$	$9493 := \frac{9^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 + 3^7}{-9^0 + 4^1 - 9^0 - 3^0}$
$9459 := \frac{9^4 + 4^3 + 5^9 - 9^6}{9^0 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^1}$	$9476 := \frac{9^3 - 4^1 - 7^0 + 6^6}{-9^0 - 4^0 + 7^0 + 6^1}$	$9494 := \frac{9^4 - 4^5 + 9^4 + 4^7}{-9^0 - 4^0 + 9^0 + 4^1}$
$9460 := \frac{9^6 + 4^1 + 6^5 - 0^0}{-9^0 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 0^1}$	$9477 := \frac{9^2 + 4^{11} + 7^0 + 7^6}{-9^0 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 7^3}$	$9496 := \frac{-9^1 + 4^8 + 9^3 + 6^3}{9^0 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 6^0}$
$9462 := \frac{9^3 + 4^8 + 6^0 - 2^5}{9^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 2^2}$	$9478 := \frac{9^4 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3}{-9^0 + 4^0 - 7^1 + 8^1}$	$9497 := \frac{-9^3 + 4^8 - 9^3 + 7^4}{9^0 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 7^0}$
$9463 := \frac{9^5 + 4^4 + 6^8 + 3^{10}}{9^1 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 3^4}$	$9479 := \frac{9^2 + 4^8 + 7^1 + 9^3}{9^0 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 9^0}$	$9498 := \frac{9^3 - 4^7 + 9^5 + 8^4}{-9^0 - 4^0 - 9^0 + 8^1}$
$9463 := \frac{9^5 + 4^4 + 6^8 + 3^{10}}{9^1 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 3^4}$	$9479 := \frac{9^2 + 4^8 + 7^1 + 9^3}{9^0 + 4^1 + 7^0 + 9^0}$	$9502 := \frac{9^8 + 5^{11} + 0^1 - 2^3}{9^4 + 5^5 - 0^0 - 2^4}$
$9464 := \frac{9^3 - 4^0 + 6^6 - 4^3}{-9^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$	$9482 := \frac{9^6 - 4^0 + 8^2 - 2^9}{-9^0 + 4^0 - 8^1 + 2^6}$	$9503 := \frac{9^3 - 5^0 - 0^0 + 3^{12}}{-9^0 - 5^2 + 0^0 + 3^4}$
$9465 := \frac{-9^2 + 4^6 + 6^7 - 5^0}{-9^0 - 4^1 + 6^2 - 5^0}$	$9483 := \frac{9^5 + 4^9 + 8^3 + 3^9}{9^1 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 3^1}$	$9504 := \frac{9^5 - 5^6 + 0^1 + 4^6}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 4^1}$
$9467 := \frac{9^2 + 4^1 + 6^0 + 7^7}{9^0 + 4^0 + 6^2 + 7^2}$	$9483 := \frac{9^5 + 4^9 + 8^3 + 3^9}{9^1 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 3^1}$	$9508 := \frac{-9^5 + 5^6 + 0^1 + 8^7}{9^3 - 5^0 + 0^1 - 8^3}$
$9467 := \frac{9^2 + 4^1 + 6^0 + 7^7}{9^0 + 4^0 + 6^2 + 7^2}$	$9484 := \frac{-9^6 + 4^0 + 8^7 + 4^8}{-9^2 - 4^1 + 8^0 + 4^4}$	$9513 := \frac{-9^4 + 5^9 + 1^0 - 3^{11}}{9^2 + 5^2 - 1^0 + 3^4}$
$9468 := \frac{9^1 - 4^0 + 6^7 + 8^4}{9^0 + 4^0 + 6^2 - 8^1}$	$9485 := \frac{9^3 + 4^9 + 8^7 + 5^8}{9^0 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 5^2}$	$9515 := \frac{9^6 - 5^6 - 1^0 - 5^7}{-9^2 + 5^0 + 1^0 + 5^3}$
$9469 := \frac{9^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 9^6}{9^1 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 9^1}$	$9485 := \frac{9^3 + 4^9 + 8^7 + 5^8}{9^0 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 5^2}$	$9521 := \frac{-9^1 + 5^8 - 2^8 + 1^0}{-9^0 + 5^2 + 2^4 + 1^0}$
$9469 := \frac{9^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 9^6}{9^1 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 9^1}$	$9486 := \frac{9^6 - 4^0 - 8^1 - 6^3}{-9^0 - 4^0 + 8^2 - 6^1}$	$9522 := \frac{9^0 + 5^9 + 2^1 + 2^{16}}{9^2 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 2^7}$

$$9522 := \frac{9^0 + 5^9 + 2^1 + 2^{16}}{9^2 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 2^7}$$

$$9523 := \frac{9^4 + 5^1 + 2^{20} + 3^{10}}{9^0 + 5^2 + 2^6 + 3^3}$$

$$9523 := \frac{9^4 + 5^1 + 2^{20} + 3^{10}}{9^0 + 5^2 + 2^6 + 3^3}$$

$$9524 := \frac{9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7}{9^0 + 5^0 + 2^2 + 4^1}$$

$$9524 := \frac{9^3 + 5^7 + 2^1 + 4^7}{9^0 + 5^0 + 2^2 + 4^1}$$

$$9525 := \frac{-9^5 - 5^2 - 2^0 + 5^7}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9526 := \frac{9^6 + 5^5 + 2^{16} + 6^2}{9^0 + 5^2 + 2^0 + 6^2}$$

$$9526 := \frac{9^6 + 5^5 + 2^{16} + 6^2}{9^0 + 5^2 + 2^0 + 6^2}$$

$$9527 := \frac{9^7 + 5^6 + 2^{11} + 7^8}{9^3 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 7^3}$$

$$9527 := \frac{9^7 + 5^6 + 2^{11} + 7^8}{9^3 + 5^1 + 2^5 + 7^3}$$

$$9528 := \frac{-9^3 + 5^6 + 2^6 + 8^4}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9529 := \frac{-9^1 - 5^4 + 2^{17} - 9^4}{9^0 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 9^1}$$

$$9530 := \frac{9^0 - 5^4 + 3^9 + 0^0}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 0^0}$$

$$9533 := \frac{-9^0 - 5^4 + 3^2 + 3^9}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9534 := \frac{9^3 + 5^9 + 3^9 + 4^0}{9^1 + 5^3 + 3^2 + 4^3}$$

$$9534 := \frac{9^3 + 5^9 + 3^9 + 4^0}{9^1 + 5^3 + 3^2 + 4^3}$$

$$9535 := \frac{-9^0 - 5^1 - 3^{10} + 5^7}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9536 := \frac{-9^5 + 5^7 - 3^1 - 6^0}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$9537 := \frac{9^0 + 5^6 + 3^5 + 7^6}{9^0 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 7^1}$$

$$9537 := \frac{9^0 + 5^6 + 3^5 + 7^6}{9^0 + 5^1 + 3^0 + 7^1}$$

$$9538 := \frac{-9^0 + 5^7 - 3^{10} + 8^0}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9539 := \frac{-9^0 + 5^3 + 3^9 - 9^3}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$9540 := \frac{-9^5 + 5^7 + 4^1 + 0^1}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$9541 := \frac{9^2 + 5^9 - 4^7 + 1^0}{9^2 + 5^3 - 4^1 + 1^0}$$

$$9542 := \frac{9^7 + 5^2 + 4^3 + 2^{17}}{9^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 2^9}$$

$$9542 := \frac{9^7 + 5^2 + 4^3 + 2^{17}}{9^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 2^9}$$

$$9543 := \frac{9^0 + 5^8 + 4^{10} + 3^{10}}{9^0 + 5^3 + 4^1 + 3^3}$$

$$9543 := \frac{9^0 + 5^8 + 4^{10} + 3^{10}}{9^0 + 5^3 + 4^1 + 3^3}$$

$$9544 := \frac{-9^5 + 5^7 - 4^1 + 4^2}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$9545 := \frac{9^2 - 5^5 - 4^8 + 5^7}{-9^0 - 5^0 + 4^1 - 5^0}$$

$$9546 := \frac{9^1 + 5^7 + 4^1 + 6^5}{9^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$9546 := \frac{9^1 + 5^7 + 4^1 + 6^5}{9^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$9547 := \frac{-9^5 - 5^2 + 4^8 + 7^6}{9^0 + 5^0 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$9548 := \frac{-9^5 + 5^5 + 4^8 - 8^2}{-9^0 - 5^0 + 4^1 - 8^0}$$

$$9549 := \frac{-9^3 - 5^1 - 4^{10} + 9^7}{9^0 + 5^3 + 4^4 + 9^1}$$

$$9550 := \frac{9^5 + 5^6 + 5^7 + 0^0}{9^1 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 0^0}$$

$$9550 := \frac{9^5 + 5^6 + 5^7 + 0^0}{9^1 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 0^0}$$

$$9551 := \frac{-9^5 + 5^2 + 5^7 + 1^0}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$9553 := \frac{-9^4 - 5^7 + 5^8 - 3^5}{9^0 + 5^1 + 5^2 + 3^0}$$

$$9556 := \frac{9^6 - 5^1 + 5^9 - 6^0}{9^1 + 5^3 + 5^3 + 6^0}$$

$$9557 := \frac{9^6 + 5^4 + 5^5 + 7^0}{9^0 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 7^2}$$

$$9557 := \frac{9^6 + 5^4 + 5^5 + 7^0}{9^0 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 7^2}$$

$$9559 := \frac{-9^0 + 5^2 + 5^6 + 9^7}{9^0 - 5^3 + 5^4 + 9^0}$$

$$9561 := \frac{9^2 + 5^8 + 6^4 - 1^0}{9^1 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 1^0}$$

$$9562 := \frac{9^8 + 5^5 + 6^5 + 2^6}{9^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 2^0}$$

$$9562 := \frac{9^8 + 5^5 + 6^5 + 2^6}{9^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 2^0}$$

$$9563 := \frac{9^2 + 5^8 + 6^4 + 3^4}{9^0 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 3^1}$$

$$9563 := \frac{9^2 + 5^8 + 6^4 + 3^4}{9^0 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 3^1}$$

$$9564 := \frac{-9^5 + 5^7 + 6^2 + 4^2}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$9565 := \frac{-9^2 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 5^4}{-9^0 - 5^0 + 6^1 + 5^0}$$

$$9566 := \frac{9^1 - 5^4 - 6^5 + 6^6}{9^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$9567 := \frac{9^4 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^6}{9^0 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 7^0}$$

$$9567 := \frac{9^4 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^6}{9^0 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 7^0}$$

$$9568 := \frac{-9^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^6}{-9^0 - 5^1 + 6^2 - 8^0}$$

$$9569 := \frac{-9^2 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 9^4}{-9^0 - 5^0 - 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$9573 := \frac{9^2 - 5^4 + 7^1 + 3^9}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9574 := \frac{-9^3 + 5^7 + 7^9 - 4^0}{9^0 + 5^3 + 7^0 + 4^6}$$

$$9575 := \frac{-9^5 + 5^2 + 7^2 + 5^7}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9576 := \frac{-9^0 - 5^1 + 7^7 - 6^0}{9^1 + 5^3 - 7^2 + 6^0}$$

$$9577 := \frac{-9^3 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 7^5}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$9578 := \frac{9^1 - 5^7 + 7^9 - 8^0}{9^3 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^1}$$

$$9579 := \frac{9^2 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 9^5}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$9581 := \frac{9^2 + 5^6 + 8^6 - 1^0}{-9^1 - 5^2 + 8^2 - 1^0}$$

$$9582 := \frac{9^1 - 5^3 - 8^5 + 2^{20}}{9^0 + 5^2 + 8^2 + 2^4}$$

$$9583 := \frac{-9^1 - 5^4 - 8^5 + 3^{11}}{9^0 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 3^0}$$

$$9584 := \frac{9^2 - 5^0 + 8^5 - 4^6}{-9^0 - 5^0 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9585 := \frac{-9^2 - 5^8 - 8^2 + 5^9}{-9^0 - 5^2 + 8^2 + 5^3}$$

$$9586 := \frac{9^4 + 5^5 - 8^2 - 6^2}{-9^0 - 5^1 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$9587 := \frac{9^0 - 5^5 - 8^4 + 7^5}{9^0 + 5^0 - 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$9588 := \frac{9^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 + 8^4}{-9^0 - 5^0 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$9589 := \frac{9^5 + 5^9 + 8^0 + 9^5}{9^1 + 5^3 + 8^0 + 9^2}$$

$$9589 := \frac{9^5 + 5^9 + 8^0 + 9^5}{9^1 + 5^3 + 8^0 + 9^2}$$

$$9593 := \frac{9^3 + 5^0 + 9^5 + 3^{15}}{-9^2 + 5^3 + 9^3 + 3^6}$$

$$9595 := \frac{9^1 + 5^1 + 9^8 + 5^6}{9^1 + 5^4 + 9^3 + 5^5}$$

$$9595 := \frac{9^1 + 5^1 + 9^8 + 5^6}{9^1 + 5^4 + 9^3 + 5^5}$$

$$9596 := \frac{9^4 - 5^4 + 9^6 - 6^0}{-9^0 - 5^2 + 9^2 + 6^0}$$

$$9597 := \frac{-9^1 + 5^5 - 9^3 + 7^5}{-9^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$9599 := \frac{9^4 - 5^5 + 9^6 + 9^7}{9^0 + 5^4 + 9^1 - 9^2}$$

$$9602 := \frac{9^3 + 6^8 + 0^0 + 2^2}{-9^1 + 6^3 + 0^1 - 2^5}$$

$$9603 := \frac{-9^3 - 6^4 + 0^1 + 3^{15}}{9^3 + 6^2 + 0^1 + 3^6}$$

$$9604 := \frac{-9^5 + 6^7 + 0^0 + 4^1}{9^0 + 6^1 + 0^1 + 4^2}$$

$$9608 := \frac{9^7 + 6^7 - 0^0 + 8^3}{9^1 + 6^1 + 0^1 + 8^3}$$

$$9612 := \frac{9^7 + 6^7 - 1^0 + 2^{18}}{9^2 + 6^3 + 1^0 + 2^8}$$

$$9614 := \frac{-9^3 + 6^5 + 1^0 + 4^9}{-9^0 - 6^2 + 1^0 + 4^3}$$

$$9616 := \frac{-9^4 + 6^8 + 1^0 + 6^9}{-9^2 + 6^1 + 1^0 + 6^4}$$

$$9618 := \frac{9^6 + 6^1 + 1^0 - 8^6}{-9^0 + 6^2 + 1^0 - 8^1}$$

$$9620 := \frac{9^5 - 6^4 - 2^5 - 0^0}{9^0 + 6^0 + 2^2 + 0^1}$$

$$9621 := \frac{9^7 + 6^5 + 2^9 + 1^0}{-9^1 - 6^1 + 2^9 + 1^0}$$

$$9622 := \frac{9^7 - 6^7 - 2^0 + 2^6}{-9^1 - 6^2 + 2^0 + 2^9}$$

$$9623 := \frac{9^3 + 6^6 + 2^0 + 3^6}{9^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$9623 := \frac{9^3 + 6^6 + 2^0 + 3^6}{9^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$9624 := \frac{9^5 - 6^4 - 2^3 - 4^0}{-9^0 + 6^0 + 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$9625 := \frac{-9^1 - 6^5 + 2^{16} - 5^0}{-9^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 5^1}$$

$$9626 := \frac{9^5 + 6^0 + 2^1 - 6^4}{-9^0 - 6^0 + 2^1 + 6^1}$$

$$9627 := \frac{9^0 - 6^5 + 2^{16} + 7^0}{-9^0 - 6^0 + 2^0 + 7^1}$$

$$9628 := \frac{9^1 - 6^5 + 2^{16} - 8^0}{-9^0 + 6^0 - 2^1 + 8^1}$$

$$9629 := \frac{-9^0 + 6^5 + 2^3 + 9^6}{9^1 + 6^1 + 2^5 + 9^1}$$

$$9630 := \frac{9^5 - 6^4 + 3^3 + 0^1}{9^0 + 6^0 + 3^1 + 0^0}$$

$$9632 := \frac{9^5 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 2^2}{9^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 2^3}$$

$$9632 := \frac{9^5 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 2^2}{9^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 2^3}$$

$$9633 := \frac{9^4 + 6^9 + 3^5 + 3^{10}}{9^2 + 6^3 + 3^3 + 3^6}$$

$$9633 := \frac{9^4 + 6^9 + 3^5 + 3^{10}}{9^2 + 6^3 + 3^3 + 3^6}$$

$$9634 := \frac{9^7 + 6^8 + 3^{13} + 4^7}{9^1 + 6^2 + 3^6 + 4^3}$$

$$9634 := \frac{9^7 + 6^8 + 3^{13} + 4^7}{9^1 + 6^2 + 3^6 + 4^3}$$

$$9635 := \frac{9^5 - 6^5 + 3^3 - 5^5}{-9^0 + 6^1 - 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9636 := \frac{9^5 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 6^5}{9^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 6^1}$$

$$9636 := \frac{9^5 + 6^3 + 3^9 + 6^5}{9^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 6^1}$$

$$9637 := \frac{9^8 + 6^9 + 3^{17} + 7^0}{9^2 + 6^4 + 3^6 + 7^5}$$

$$9637 := \frac{9^8 + 6^9 + 3^{17} + 7^0}{9^2 + 6^4 + 3^6 + 7^5}$$

$$9638 := \frac{-9^3 + 6^4 + 3^{12} - 8^6}{-9^0 + 6^0 + 3^3 + 8^0}$$

$$9639 := \frac{9^2 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 9^5}{9^0 + 6^1 + 3^1 + 9^0}$$

$$9639 := \frac{9^2 + 6^6 + 3^5 + 9^5}{9^0 + 6^1 + 3^1 + 9^0}$$

$$9640 := \frac{9^2 - 6^5 + 4^8 - 0^0}{9^0 + 6^0 + 4^1 + 0^1}$$

$$9642 := \frac{9^6 + 6^7 + 4^0 + 2^{13}}{9^0 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 2^5}$$

$$9642 := \frac{9^6 + 6^7 + 4^0 + 2^{13}}{9^0 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 2^5}$$

$$9643 := \frac{9^2 + 6^5 + 4^9 + 3^1}{9^1 + 6^1 + 4^1 + 3^2}$$

$$9643 := \frac{9^2 + 6^5 + 4^9 + 3^1}{9^1 + 6^1 + 4^1 + 3^2}$$

$$9644 := \frac{9^6 - 6^0 + 4^1 - 4^5}{9^0 - 6^1 - 4^1 + 4^3}$$

$$9646 := \frac{9^{10} + 6^0 - 4^{14} + 6^{13}}{-9^0 + 6^5 + 4^4 + 6^8}$$

$$9647 := \frac{9^7 - 6^0 - 4^8 - 7^2}{9^2 + 6^0 + 4^3 + 7^3}$$

$$9648 := \frac{-9^2 + 6^7 + 4^0 - 8^2}{-9^0 + 6^1 + 4^2 + 8^1}$$

$$9649 := \frac{-9^3 - 6^0 - 4^2 + 9^6}{9^1 + 6^2 + 4^0 + 9^1}$$

$$9650 := \frac{9^4 - 6^2 + 5^5 + 0^1}{-9^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 0^1}$$

$$9651 := \frac{9^4 - 6^2 + 5^5 + 1^0}{9^0 - 6^1 + 5^1 + 1^0}$$

$$9652 := \frac{9^4 + 6^1 + 5^8 + 2^{13}}{9^0 + 6^2 + 5^0 + 2^2}$$

$$9652 := \frac{9^4 + 6^1 + 5^8 + 2^{13}}{9^0 + 6^2 + 5^0 + 2^2}$$

$$9653 := \frac{9^4 - 6^1 + 5^5 - 3^3}{-9^0 + 6^1 - 5^0 - 3^1}$$

$$9654 := \frac{9^3 + 6^5 + 5^7 + 4^4}{9^0 + 6^1 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$9655 := \frac{9^3 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 5^7}{9^0 + 6^1 + 5^0 + 5^1}$$

$$9655 := \frac{9^3 + 6^6 + 5^1 + 5^7}{9^0 + 6^1 + 5^0 + 5^1}$$

$$9656 := \frac{9^4 + 6^1 + 5^5 - 6^2}{-9^0 + 6^0 - 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$9657 := \frac{9^0 - 6^5 + 5^4 + 7^5}{-9^0 - 6^1 + 5^0 + 7^1}$$

$$9658 := \frac{9^4 - 6^2 + 5^5 + 8^1}{-9^0 - 6^0 - 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$9659 := \frac{9^1 - 6^2 + 5^5 + 9^4}{-9^0 - 6^1 - 5^0 + 9^1}$$

$$9662 := \frac{9^6 + 6^0 - 6^2 + 2^2}{9^1 + 6^1 + 6^2 + 2^2}$$

$$9663 := \frac{9^7 + 6^3 + 6^3 + 3^{14}}{9^1 + 6^2 + 6^3 + 3^6}$$

$$9663 := \frac{9^7 + 6^3 + 6^3 + 3^{14}}{9^1 + 6^2 + 6^3 + 3^6}$$

$$9664 := \frac{9^2 - 6^0 - 6^4 + 4^9}{9^1 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 4^2}$$

$$9665 := \frac{9^6 - 6^3 - 6^7 + 5^0}{9^1 + 6^1 + 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$9667 := \frac{9^7 + 6^5 - 6^8 + 7^6}{9^2 + 6^2 + 6^3 + 7^0}$$

$$9669 := \frac{9^5 - 6^3 + 6^7 + 9^6}{9^1 + 6^2 + 6^2 + 9^1}$$

$$9670 := \frac{-9^1 + 6^{10} + 7^3 + 0^1}{9^4 + 6^2 - 7^3 - 0^0}$$

$$9671 := \frac{9^6 + 6^9 - 7^2 - 1^0}{-9^1 - 6^4 + 7^4 + 1^0}$$

$$9672 := \frac{9^6 + 6^1 + 7^0 + 2^9}{9^0 + 6^0 + 7^2 + 2^2}$$

$$9672 := \frac{9^6 + 6^1 + 7^0 + 2^9}{9^0 + 6^0 + 7^2 + 2^2}$$

$$9673 := \frac{9^2 + 6^5 + 7^6 + 3^5}{-9^0 + 6^1 - 7^0 + 3^2}$$

$$9674 := \frac{9^2 + 6^5 + 7^6 + 4^4}{9^0 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 4^1}$$

$$9674 := \frac{9^2 + 6^5 + 7^6 + 4^4}{9^0 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 4^1}$$

$$9675 := \frac{-9^2 - 6^5 + 7^5 + 5^7}{9^0 + 6^1 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9676 := \frac{-9^1 + 6^6 + 7^4 + 6^7}{-9^0 + 6^1 - 7^1 + 6^2}$$

$$9677 := \frac{9^6 + 6^6 + 7^6 + 7^7}{-9^1 + 6^3 - 7^0 - 7^2}$$

$$9678 := \frac{-9^3 - 6^4 + 7^6 + 8^3}{9^1 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9679 := \frac{-9^2 - 6^5 + 7^5 + 9^3}{-9^0 - 6^1 - 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$9680 := \frac{9^6 - 6^6 - 8^6 - 0^0}{9^1 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 0^1}$$

$$9682 := \frac{9^3 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 2^{10}}{9^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$9682 := \frac{9^3 + 6^6 + 8^0 + 2^{10}}{9^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$9683 := \frac{-9^3 - 6^0 + 8^6 + 3^3}{9^1 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 3^2}$$

$$9684 := \frac{-9^1 + 6^8 + 8^7 + 4^0}{-9^2 + 6^3 - 8^0 + 4^4}$$

$$9685 := \frac{9^4 + 6^2 + 8^5 - 5^4}{9^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9686 := \frac{9^6 + 6^0 - 8^6 - 6^5}{-9^1 - 6^0 + 8^0 + 6^2}$$

$$9687 := \frac{9^4 - 6^2 + 8^6 - 7^5}{-9^0 + 6^2 - 8^1 - 7^0}$$

$$9688 := \frac{9^3 - 6^4 - 8^0 + 8^6}{-9^1 + 6^2 - 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9689 := \frac{-9^3 + 6^5 + 8^4 + 9^6}{-9^0 - 6^1 + 8^2 - 9^0}$$

$$9692 := \frac{-9^3 - 6^5 + 9^7 + 2^{15}}{-9^0 - 6^1 - 9^1 + 2^9}$$

$$9693 := \frac{9^3 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 3^9}{9^0 + 6^1 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9694 := \frac{9^1 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 4^5}{9^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9694 := \frac{9^1 + 6^5 + 9^5 + 4^5}{9^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9696 := \frac{9^1 + 6^1 + 9^6 - 6^6}{-9^0 + 6^1 + 9^1 + 6^2}$$

$$9697 := \frac{9^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 + 7^4}{-9^0 - 6^1 + 9^0 + 7^1}$$

$$9698 := \frac{-9^0 - 6^3 - 9^2 + 8^6}{9^1 + 6^0 + 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$9699 := \frac{-9^5 + 6^5 - 9^5 + 9^9}{-9^2 + 6^6 - 9^2 - 9^4}$$

$$9704 := \frac{-9^1 + 7^4 + 0^1 + 4^8}{9^0 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9706 := \frac{9^6 - 7^5 + 0^1 - 6^3}{9^1 + 7^1 + 0^0 + 6^2}$$

$$9707 := \frac{-9^1 + 7^6 + 0^0 + 7^8}{-9^2 + 7^3 + 0^0 + 7^3}$$

$$9719 := \frac{-9^3 - 7^1 + 1^0 + 9^5}{-9^0 - 7^0 - 1^0 + 9^1}$$

$$9721 := \frac{9^1 + 7^8 - 2^8 - 1^0}{9^2 - 7^0 + 2^9 + 1^0}$$

$$9722 := \frac{9^4 + 7^6 + 2^7 + 2^{11}}{9^0 + 7^1 + 2^0 + 2^2}$$

$$9722 := \frac{9^4 + 7^6 + 2^7 + 2^{11}}{9^0 + 7^1 + 2^0 + 2^2}$$

$$9723 := \frac{9^4 + 7^6 + 2^1 + 3^7}{9^0 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 3^2}$$

$$9724 := \frac{9^3 + 7^9 + 2^3 + 4^4}{9^0 + 7^2 + 2^2 + 4^6}$$

$$9724 := \frac{9^3 + 7^9 + 2^3 + 4^4}{9^0 + 7^2 + 2^2 + 4^6}$$

$$9725 := \frac{9^4 + 7^4 + 2^{19} + 5^8}{9^1 + 7^2 + 2^5 + 5^1}$$

$$9726 := \frac{9^5 + 7^1 + 2^{19} + 6^3}{9^0 + 7^1 + 2^4 + 6^2}$$

$$9726 := \frac{9^5 + 7^1 + 2^{19} + 6^3}{9^0 + 7^1 + 2^4 + 6^2}$$

$$9727 := \frac{-9^4 - 7^1 - 2^9 + 7^5}{-9^0 - 7^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$9728 := \frac{9^5 + 7^3 + 2^{13} + 8^3}{9^0 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 8^0}$$

$$9728 := \frac{9^5 + 7^3 + 2^{13} + 8^3}{9^0 + 7^0 + 2^2 + 8^0}$$

$$9729 := \frac{9^4 + 7^5 - 2^8 + 9^6}{9^1 + 7^1 + 2^5 + 9^1}$$

$$9732 := \frac{-9^6 - 7^3 + 3^{17} + 2^0}{9^2 + 7^2 - 3^9 + 2^{15}}$$

$$9733 := \frac{-9^3 + 7^4 + 3^9 + 3^{13}}{9^1 + 7^2 + 3^3 + 3^4}$$

$$9734 := \frac{-9^2 + 7^7 - 3^{12} - 4^0}{9^0 + 7^0 + 3^3 + 4^0}$$

$$9735 := \frac{-9^2 - 7^1 + 3^9 - 5^3}{-9^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9737 := \frac{-9^3 - 7^2 - 3^3 + 7^6}{9^0 + 7^0 + 3^1 + 7^1}$$

$$9739 := \frac{9^1 + 7^5 + 3^{13} + 9^6}{9^2 + 7^2 + 3^2 + 9^2}$$

$$9739 := \frac{9^1 + 7^5 + 3^{13} + 9^6}{9^2 + 7^2 + 3^2 + 9^2}$$

$$9742 := \frac{9^0 + 7^4 + 4^4 + 2^{16}}{9^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 2^2}$$

$$9742 := \frac{9^0 + 7^4 + 4^4 + 2^{16}}{9^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 2^2}$$

$$9743 := \frac{-9^2 + 7^0 + 4^7 - 3^8}{-9^0 - 7^0 + 4^1 - 3^0}$$

$$9744 := \frac{9^5 + 7^3 + 4^2 + 4^9}{9^1 + 7^1 + 4^0 + 4^2}$$

$$9744 := \frac{9^5 + 7^3 + 4^2 + 4^9}{9^1 + 7^1 + 4^0 + 4^2}$$

$$9745 := \frac{-9^4 - 7^3 + 4^5 + 5^6}{-9^0 - 7^0 + 4^1 - 5^0}$$

$$9746 := \frac{-9^3 + 7^6 - 4^1 + 6^2}{9^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 6^1}$$

$$9747 := \frac{-9^0 + 7^1 + 4^8 - 7^5}{-9^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 7^0}$$

$$9748 := \frac{9^5 + 7^5 - 4^6 - 8^5}{9^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9749 := \frac{-9^2 + 7^1 + 4^7 - 9^4}{-9^0 - 7^0 + 4^1 - 9^0}$$

$$9752 := \frac{-9^0 + 7^6 - 5^4 + 2^0}{9^1 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$9753 := \frac{-9^2 + 7^6 - 5^0 - 3^{10}}{9^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 3^1}$$

$$9754 := \frac{9^8 + 7^1 - 5^9 - 4^0}{9^3 + 7^3 + 5^5 + 4^2}$$

$$9755 := \frac{-9^1 + 7^2 - 5^3 + 5^7}{9^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 5^1}$$

$$9756 := \frac{-9^3 + 7^3 + 5^8 + 6^0}{9^1 + 7^1 + 5^2 - 6^0}$$

$$9757 := \frac{-9^0 - 7^0 + 5^8 - 7^3}{9^0 + 7^1 + 5^2 + 7^1}$$

$$9759 := \frac{-9^2 - 7^5 - 5^5 + 9^5}{9^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$9760 := \frac{9^3 + 7^5 - 6^5 + 0^1}{-9^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 0^1}$$

$$9761 := \frac{9^3 + 7^5 - 6^5 + 1^0}{9^0 - 7^1 + 6^1 + 1^0}$$

$$9762 := \frac{9^6 + 7^1 + 6^4 + 2^{17}}{9^1 + 7^1 + 6^2 + 2^4}$$

$$9762 := \frac{9^6 + 7^1 + 6^4 + 2^{17}}{9^1 + 7^1 + 6^2 + 2^4}$$

$$9763 := \frac{9^2 + 7^6 + 6^5 + 3^{11}}{9^1 + 7^1 + 6^1 + 3^2}$$

$$9763 := \frac{9^2 + 7^6 + 6^5 + 3^{11}}{9^1 + 7^1 + 6^1 + 3^2}$$

$$9764 := \frac{9^3 + 7^5 - 6^5 + 4^1}{-9^0 - 7^0 - 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9765 := \frac{9^3 + 7^5 - 6^5 + 5^1}{9^0 + 7^0 - 6^1 + 5^1}$$

$$9766 := \frac{9^2 + 7^2 + 6^1 + 6^8}{9^2 + 7^2 + 6^1 + 6^2}$$

$$9766 := \frac{9^2 + 7^2 + 6^1 + 6^8}{9^2 + 7^2 + 6^1 + 6^2}$$

$$9767 := \frac{9^3 + 7^1 - 6^5 + 7^5}{-9^0 + 7^0 - 6^1 + 7^1}$$

$$9768 := \frac{9^3 + 7^5 - 6^5 + 8^1}{-9^0 - 7^1 + 6^0 + 8^1}$$

$$9769 := \frac{9^1 + 7^5 - 6^5 + 9^3}{-9^0 - 7^0 - 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$9772 := \frac{-9^3 + 7^3 + 7^6 + 2^0}{9^1 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$9773 := \frac{-9^2 - 7^1 - 7^2 + 3^9}{-9^0 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9775 := \frac{9^2 + 7^7 + 7^8 + 5^7}{9^0 + 7^1 + 7^2 + 5^4}$$

$$9775 := \frac{9^2 + 7^7 + 7^8 + 5^7}{9^0 + 7^1 + 7^2 + 5^4}$$

$$9776 := \frac{9^5 - 7^2 - 7^3 - 6^0}{-9^0 - 7^0 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$9779 := \frac{9^2 - 7^1 + 7^6 - 9^5}{-9^0 - 7^0 - 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$9782 := \frac{9^3 + 7^8 + 8^1 + 2^{19}}{9^2 + 7^2 + 8^0 + 2^9}$$

$$9782 := \frac{9^3 + 7^8 + 8^1 + 2^{19}}{9^2 + 7^2 + 8^0 + 2^9}$$

$$9783 := \frac{9^7 + 7^6 + 8^5 + 3^{15}}{9^3 + 7^0 + 8^3 + 3^6}$$

$$9783 := \frac{9^7 + 7^6 + 8^5 + 3^{15}}{9^3 + 7^0 + 8^3 + 3^6}$$

$$9784 := \frac{9^1 - 7^4 + 8^5 - 4^5}{-9^0 - 7^0 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9785 := \frac{9^5 - 7^3 - 8^0 + 5^1}{-9^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 5^1}$$

$$9786 := \frac{-9^1 + 7^6 + 8^1 - 6^3}{9^1 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$9787 := \frac{9^5 + 7^3 + 8^6 + 7^7}{-9^3 + 7^5 - 8^5 + 7^5}$$

$$9788 := \frac{-9^5 + 7^6 + 8^2 + 8^2}{-9^0 + 7^1 - 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9789 := \frac{9^4 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 9^5}{-9^0 - 7^0 + 8^1 + 9^0}$$

$$9790 := \frac{-9^1 + 7^5 + 9^6 + 0^0}{-9^0 + 7^2 + 9^1 - 0^0}$$

$$9793 := \frac{-9^1 - 7^1 - 9^2 + 3^9}{-9^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9795 := \frac{-9^1 + 7^7 - 9^3 - 5^2}{9^0 + 7^0 + 9^2 + 5^0}$$

$$9797 := \frac{-9^1 - 7^3 + 9^5 + 7^6}{9^0 + 7^0 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$9798 := \frac{9^2 - 7^3 + 9^5 + 8^0}{-9^0 - 7^0 + 9^1 - 8^0}$$

$$9802 := \frac{9^5 + 8^0 + 0^1 + 2^{20}}{9^2 - 8^0 + 0^0 + 2^5}$$

$$9806 := \frac{-9^7 + 8^3 + 0^0 + 6^9}{-9^1 + 8^3 + 0^0 + 6^2}$$

$$9813 := \frac{9^2 - 8^7 - 1^0 + 3^{16}}{9^2 + 8^4 - 1^0 - 3^1}$$

$$9814 := \frac{-9^4 - 8^1 - 1^0 + 4^7}{-9^0 - 8^0 - 1^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9815 := \frac{-9^4 + 8^7 - 1^0 + 5^1}{9^2 + 8^1 - 1^0 + 5^3}$$

$$9816 := \frac{9^5 + 8^2 - 1^0 - 6^3}{9^1 - 8^0 - 1^0 - 6^0}$$

$$9820 := \frac{9^5 - 8^0 - 2^7 + 0^1}{9^0 + 8^0 + 2^2 + 0^1}$$

$$9821 := \frac{-9^4 - 8^0 + 2^{14} - 1^0}{-9^0 - 8^0 + 2^1 + 1^0}$$

$$9822 := \frac{-9^4 + 8^0 - 2^1 + 2^{14}}{-9^0 - 8^0 + 2^0 + 2^1}$$

$$9823 := \frac{-9^0 + 8^0 + 2^{14} - 3^8}{-9^0 - 8^0 + 2^1 + 3^0}$$

$$9824 := \frac{-9^4 - 8^0 + 2^1 + 4^7}{-9^0 - 8^0 - 2^0 + 4^1}$$

$$9825 := \frac{9^0 + 8^0 + 2^{11} + 5^9}{9^1 + 8^0 + 2^6 + 5^3}$$

$$9825 := \frac{9^0 + 8^0 + 2^{11} + 5^9}{9^1 + 8^0 + 2^6 + 5^3}$$

$$9826 := \frac{9^0 + 8^0 + 2^{11} + 6^5}{-9^0 - 8^0 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$9827 := \frac{9^1 + 8^4 + 2^{17} + 7^4}{9^0 + 8^1 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$9827 := \frac{9^1 + 8^4 + 2^{17} + 7^4}{9^0 + 8^1 + 2^2 + 7^0}$$

$$9828 := \frac{9^4 - 8^0 - 2^4 + 8^5}{9^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9829 := \frac{9^5 + 8^4 + 2^7 + 9^8}{9^2 + 8^4 + 2^7 + 9^2}$$

$$9829 := \frac{9^5 + 8^4 + 2^7 + 9^8}{9^2 + 8^4 + 2^7 + 9^2}$$

$$9830 := \frac{-9^1 + 8^5 + 3^8 + 0^1}{9^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 0^0}$$

$$9832 := \frac{9^0 + 8^1 - 3^8 + 2^{14}}{-9^0 - 8^0 + 3^0 + 2^1}$$

$$9833 := \frac{-9^1 + 8^0 - 3^2 + 3^9}{-9^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9834 := \frac{9^4 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 4^1}{9^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$9834 := \frac{9^4 + 8^5 + 3^1 + 4^1}{9^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$9835 := \frac{9^7 + 8^6 + 3^{11} + 5^3}{9^1 + 8^3 + 3^2 + 5^0}$$

$$9835 := \frac{9^7 + 8^6 + 3^{11} + 5^3}{9^1 + 8^3 + 3^2 + 5^0}$$

$$9836 := \frac{9^1 + 8^5 + 3^8 + 6^1}{9^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$9836 := \frac{9^1 + 8^5 + 3^8 + 6^1}{9^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$9837 := \frac{-9^0 - 8^0 + 3^9 - 7^1}{-9^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$9838 := \frac{9^2 + 8^5 + 3^{19} + 8^6}{9^5 + 8^1 + 3^{10} + 8^2}$$

$$9838 := \frac{9^2 + 8^5 + 3^{19} + 8^6}{9^5 + 8^1 + 3^{10} + 8^2}$$

$$9839 := \frac{-9^1 - 8^0 - 3^9 + 9^5}{9^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$9840 := \frac{-9^4 + 8^2 + 4^8 + 0^0}{9^0 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 0^1}$$

$$9841 := \frac{9^5 - 8^0 - 4^0 - 1^0}{9^0 + 8^1 - 4^1 + 1^0}$$

$$9842 := \frac{9^5 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}{-9^0 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 2^1}$$

$$9843 := \frac{9^4 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 3^3}{9^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9843 := \frac{9^4 + 8^5 + 4^2 + 3^3}{9^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9845 := \frac{-9^5 + 8^5 + 4^8 + 5^3}{9^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9846 := \frac{9^5 - 8^0 + 4^3 - 6^2}{9^0 + 8^1 - 4^1 + 6^0}$$

$$9847 := \frac{9^7 + 8^7 + 4^7 + 7^7}{9^1 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 7^1}$$

$$9847 := \frac{9^7 + 8^7 + 4^7 + 7^7}{9^1 + 8^3 + 4^4 + 7^1}$$

$$9848 := \frac{9^4 - 8^0 + 4^3 + 8^5}{9^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$9849 := \frac{-9^2 - 8^4 + 4^{10} + 9^6}{-9^0 + 8^2 + 4^2 + 9^2}$$

$$9852 := \frac{-9^0 + 8^4 + 5^6 - 2^4}{-9^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$9853 := \frac{9^2 + 8^0 + 5^3 + 3^{11}}{9^1 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 3^1}$$

$$9853 := \frac{9^2 + 8^0 + 5^3 + 3^{11}}{9^1 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 3^1}$$

$$9854 := \frac{-9^1 + 8^4 + 5^6 - 4^1}{-9^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$9855 := \frac{-9^1 + 8^2 + 5^4 + 5^{10}}{9^3 + 8^3 - 5^3 - 5^3}$$

$$9856 := \frac{-9^2 + 8^5 - 5^5 + 6^1}{-9^0 - 8^0 - 5^0 + 6^1}$$

$$9857 := \frac{9^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 7^0}{9^0 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 7^0}$$

$$9857 := \frac{9^3 + 8^0 + 5^7 + 7^0}{9^0 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 7^0}$$

$$9858 := \frac{9^5 + 8^4 + 5^2 + 8^6}{-9^0 + 8^0 + 5^2 + 8^1}$$

$$9859 := \frac{9^2 - 8^0 + 5^2 + 9^5}{-9^0 - 8^0 - 5^0 + 9^1}$$

$$9862 := \frac{9^5 + 8^0 - 6^1 + 2^7}{-9^0 - 8^0 + 6^1 + 2^1}$$

$$9863 := \frac{-9^0 + 8^1 + 6^2 + 3^9}{-9^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9864 := \frac{9^7 + 8^5 - 6^0 - 4^{11}}{-9^0 - 8^0 + 6^0 + 4^3}$$

$$9865 := \frac{9^4 + 8^5 + 6^1 + 5^3}{9^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9865 := \frac{9^4 + 8^5 + 6^1 + 5^3}{9^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9867 := \frac{9^5 - 8^2 + 6^3 + 7^0}{-9^0 - 8^0 + 6^0 + 7^1}$$

$$9869 := \frac{-9^5 + 8^7 - 6^7 + 9^6}{9^2 + 8^2 + 6^1 + 9^2}$$

$$9872 := \frac{9^5 + 8^5 + 7^7 + 2^{17}}{9^1 + 8^2 + 7^0 + 2^5}$$

$$9872 := \frac{9^5 + 8^5 + 7^7 + 2^{17}}{9^1 + 8^2 + 7^0 + 2^5}$$

$$9873 := \frac{9^1 - 8^4 + 7^7 + 3^1}{9^1 + 8^2 + 7^0 + 3^2}$$

$$9874 := \frac{9^7 + 8^6 + 7^9 + 4^{10}}{9^1 + 8^4 + 7^3 + 4^4}$$

$$9874 := \frac{9^7 + 8^6 + 7^9 + 4^{10}}{9^1 + 8^4 + 7^3 + 4^4}$$

$$9875 := \frac{9^5 + 8^5 + 7^5 + 5^0}{9^0 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9875 := \frac{9^5 + 8^5 + 7^5 + 5^0}{9^0 + 8^1 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$9876 := \frac{9^5 - 8^1 - 7^0 + 6^3}{-9^0 - 8^0 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$9877 := \frac{-9^3 + 8^5 - 7^1 - 7^4}{9^0 + 8^1 + 7^0 - 7^1}$$

$$9878 := \frac{-9^5 - 8^5 - 7^4 + 8^6}{9^0 + 8^0 + 7^1 + 8^1}$$

$$9879 := \frac{-9^3 + 8^4 - 7^2 + 9^4}{-9^0 - 8^1 + 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$9882 := \frac{9^3 + 8^0 + 8^8 - 2^{13}}{9^3 + 8^1 - 8^2 + 2^{10}}$$

$$9883 := \frac{9^2 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 3^9}{-9^0 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$9884 := \frac{9^5 - 8^0 + 8^3 - 4^4}{9^0 + 8^0 + 8^1 - 4^1}$$

$$9885 := \frac{9^0 + 8^1 + 8^4 + 5^9}{9^0 + 8^1 + 8^2 + 5^3}$$

$$9885 := \frac{9^0 + 8^1 + 8^4 + 5^9}{9^0 + 8^1 + 8^2 + 5^3}$$

$$9886 := \frac{9^4 - 8^0 + 8^5 + 6^3}{9^0 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$9887 := \frac{9^1 - 8^4 + 8^6 + 7^6}{-9^1 - 8^0 - 8^0 + 7^2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9889 &:= \frac{9^4 + 8^3 + 8^5 + 9^5}{-9^0 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 9^1} \\
 9892 &:= \frac{-9^4 + 8^2 + 9^5 - 2^{15}}{-9^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 2^0} \\
 9893 &:= \frac{9^0 - 8^6 + 9^6 - 3^7}{9^0 + 8^1 + 9^1 + 3^2} \\
 9894 &:= \frac{-9^1 + 8^5 + 9^4 + 4^4}{9^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 4^0} \\
 9896 &:= \frac{9^0 - 8^3 - 9^4 + 6^6}{9^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 6^0} \\
 9897 &:= \frac{-9^1 + 8^5 - 9^2 + 7^5}{-9^0 + 8^1 - 9^0 - 7^0} \\
 9904 &:= \frac{9^2 - 9^4 + 0^1 + 4^7}{-9^0 - 9^0 - 0^0 + 4^1} \\
 9904 &:= \frac{9^2 - 9^4 + 0^1 + 4^7}{-9^0 - 9^0 - 0^0 + 4^1} \\
 9921 &:= \frac{-9^5 + 9^7 + 2^{19} + 1^0}{9^1 + 9^1 + 2^9 - 1^0} \\
 9922 &:= \frac{9^4 + 9^6 - 2^7 - 2^{17}}{-9^0 + 9^1 + 2^0 + 2^5} \\
 9923 &:= \frac{9^2 + 9^2 + 2^0 + 3^9}{-9^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 3^0} \\
 9924 &:= \frac{-9^3 + 9^4 - 2^2 + 4^6}{-9^0 - 9^0 - 2^0 + 4^1} \\
 9925 &:= \frac{-9^3 + 9^4 + 2^{18} - 5^0}{9^0 + 9^1 + 2^4 + 5^0} \\
 9926 &:= \frac{9^3 + 9^3 + 2^{20} + 6^8}{9^1 + 9^1 + 2^8 + 6^0} \\
 9926 &:= \frac{9^3 + 9^3 + 2^{20} + 6^8}{9^1 + 9^1 + 2^8 + 6^0} \\
 9927 &:= \frac{-9^3 + 9^4 + 2^{12} - 7^0}{-9^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 7^0} \\
 9928 &:= \frac{-9^3 + 9^4 + 2^{13} - 8^4}{-9^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 8^0} \\
 9929 &:= \frac{9^0 - 9^3 + 2^{12} + 9^4}{-9^0 - 9^0 + 2^1 + 9^0}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9933 &:= \frac{9^3 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 3^9}{9^0 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 3^1} \\
 9933 &:= \frac{9^3 + 9^5 + 3^1 + 3^9}{9^0 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 3^1} \\
 9934 &:= \frac{9^3 - 9^6 + 3^{15} - 4^0}{9^3 + 9^3 - 3^1 - 4^3} \\
 9935 &:= \frac{9^2 + 9^2 + 3^9 + 5^2}{-9^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 5^0} \\
 9937 &:= \frac{-9^4 - 9^4 + 3^{12} + 7^6}{-9^0 - 9^1 + 3^4 - 7^1} \\
 9942 &:= \frac{-9^1 - 9^4 + 4^7 + 2^7}{-9^0 - 9^0 + 4^0 + 2^1} \\
 9943 &:= \frac{9^3 - 9^4 + 4^7 + 3^{10}}{9^0 + 9^0 + 4^1 + 3^0} \\
 9944 &:= \frac{-9^3 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 4^6}{-9^0 - 9^0 - 4^0 + 4^1} \\
 9946 &:= \frac{9^1 + 9^6 - 4^6 - 6^3}{-9^0 - 9^1 + 4^3 - 6^0} \\
 9947 &:= \frac{9^3 + 9^4 + 4^4 + 7^4}{-9^0 - 9^0 + 4^1 - 7^0} \\
 9948 &:= \frac{-9^2 + 9^7 + 4^{11} - 8^4}{-9^3 - 9^4 + 4^6 + 8^4} \\
 9949 &:= \frac{-9^0 - 9^2 + 4^9 + 9^4}{9^0 + 9^0 + 4^2 + 9^1} \\
 9955 &:= \frac{9^2 + 9^5 - 5^2 + 5^4}{-9^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 5^1} \\
 9957 &:= \frac{-9^1 - 9^1 + 5^5 + 7^5}{-9^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 7^0} \\
 9959 &:= \frac{-9^0 + 9^2 + 5^4 + 9^5}{-9^0 - 9^0 - 5^0 + 9^1} \\
 9962 &:= \frac{9^1 - 9^4 + 6^6 - 2^8}{9^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 2^0} \\
 9963 &:= \frac{9^4 + 9^6 + 6^5 + 3^7}{9^0 + 9^1 + 6^2 + 3^2} \\
 9964 &:= \frac{-9^3 + 9^4 + 6^2 + 4^6}{-9^0 - 9^0 - 6^0 + 4^1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9965 &:= \frac{9^2 + 9^9 - 6^{11} + 5^0}{9^2 - 9^3 - 6^1 + 5^5} \\
 9966 &:= \frac{-9^2 + 9^8 - 6^4 + 6^5}{-9^3 + 9^4 - 6^3 - 6^4} \\
 9967 &:= \frac{9^5 + 9^6 - 6^2 - 7^4}{-9^1 + 9^2 - 6^1 - 7^1} \\
 9968 &:= \frac{-9^4 + 9^5 + 6^3 - 8^5}{-9^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 8^0} \\
 9971 &:= \frac{9^3 + 9^5 + 7^2 - 1^0}{-9^0 - 9^0 + 7^1 + 1^0} \\
 9973 &:= \frac{9^0 - 9^2 + 7^3 + 3^9}{-9^0 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 3^0} \\
 9975 &:= \frac{9^1 + 9^1 + 7^5 + 5^5}{-9^0 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 5^0} \\
 9976 &:= \frac{9^4 + 9^4 + 7^5 - 6^0}{-9^0 - 9^0 - 7^0 + 6^1} \\
 9977 &:= \frac{9^7 + 9^8 - 7^0 + 7^2}{9^0 - 9^1 + 7^4 + 7^4} \\
 9982 &:= \frac{9^3 + 9^6 - 8^3 - 2^{18}}{9^0 + 9^1 + 8^0 + 2^4} \\
 9983 &:= \frac{9^0 + 9^6 - 8^6 + 3^5}{9^0 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 3^2} \\
 9984 &:= \frac{9^4 - 9^5 + 8^1 + 4^9}{9^1 + 9^1 - 8^0 + 4^1} \\
 9985 &:= \frac{9^5 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 5^8}{9^1 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 5^2} \\
 9985 &:= \frac{9^5 + 9^5 + 8^3 + 5^8}{9^1 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 5^2} \\
 9986 &:= \frac{9^6 + 9^8 + 8^8 + 6^1}{9^0 + 9^4 - 8^3 - 6^1} \\
 9987 &:= \frac{9^1 + 9^6 - 8^6 + 7^3}{9^1 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 7^0} \\
 9988 &:= \frac{9^1 - 9^4 + 8^4 + 8^6}{9^0 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 8^1}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.5 Five Digits Numbers

$$10032 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 0^0 + 3^{12} + 2^8}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 0^1 - 3^2 + 2^6}$$

$$10082 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 0^1 - 8^1 + 2^{17}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 2^1}$$

$$10122 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 1^0 + 2^9 + 2^{17}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 2^3}$$

$$10145 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 1^0 + 4^8 + 5^6}{1^0 + 0^0 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$10153 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 1^0 + 5^4 + 3^9}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10176 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 6^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10222 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 2^4 + 2^{11} + 2^{13}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10223 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^8 - 2^{13} + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10224 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{11} + 2^{13} - 4^2}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$10225 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 2^9 + 2^{16} + 5^7}{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$10227 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{14} + 2^{18} - 7^4}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 2^4 + 7^1}$$

$$10229 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^{11} + 2^{13} - 9^1}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 9^0}$$

$$10232 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{11} - 3^2 + 2^{13}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10233 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{10} - 3^5 + 3^9}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10234 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{18} + 3^{10} + 4^9}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 2^1 - 3^1 + 4^3}$$

$$10235 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{15} - 3^7 + 5^3}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$10236 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^5 + 3^{13} - 6^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 6^3}$$

$$10237 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 7^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$10238 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{14} - 3^1 + 8^4}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 2^0 - 3^1 + 8^1}$$

$$10239 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 9^6}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 9^1}$$

$$10240 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{12} + 4^7 + 0^1}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$$

$$10241 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{12} + 4^7 + 1^0}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 + 1^0}$$

$$10242 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{10} + 4^5 + 2^{13}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10243 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 3^{13}}{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^6 + 4^3 + 3^3}$$

$$10244 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^3 + 4^6 + 4^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 2^0 + 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$10245 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{14} + 4^{11} + 5^1}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^2}$$

$$10246 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^8 + 6^6}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$10247 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 2^4 - 4^9 + 7^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^3 + 7^3}$$

$$10248 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 8^4}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 + 8^0}$$

$$10249 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^{10} + 9^4}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^2 + 4^2 + 9^2}$$

$$10252 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{12} + 5^2 + 2^{14}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$10253 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{13} - 5^3 + 3^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10254 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{19} + 5^5 + 4^9}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^3 + 5^1 + 4^3}$$

$$10255 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{16} + 5^5 + 5^5}{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^2 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$10256 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{16} + 5^4 + 6^6}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 5^0 + 6^1}$$

$$10257 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{19} + 5^6 - 7^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 7^2}$$

$$10258 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{19} - 5^5 + 8^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^5 + 5^2 - 8^0}$$

$$10262 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{13} + 6^3 + 2^{20}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 6^2 + 2^6}$$

$$10263 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^{11} - 6^6 + 3^{13}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^5 + 6^2 + 3^4}$$

$$10264 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{16} - 6^6 + 4^{10}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 6^2 + 4^3}$$

$$10265 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^{19} - 6^3 - 5^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^2 + 6^1 + 5^0}$$

$$10266 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{10} - 6^5 + 6^9}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{10} - 6^1 - 6^2}$$

$$10267 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{17} - 6^0 + 7^4}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^2 + 6^1 + 7^0}$$

$$10269 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{16} - 6^3 + 9^4}{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^2 + 6^0 + 9^0}$$

$$10272 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 2^6 + 7^4 + 2^{17}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 2^3}$$

$$10273 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{14} - 7^4 + 3^8}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10274 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 2^6 + 7^8 - 4^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^8 + 7^2 + 4^4}$$

$$10275 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{18} - 7^3 + 5^6}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 5^2}$$

$$10276 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^5 + 7^8 + 6^0}{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^0 + 7^3 + 6^3}$$

$$10279 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^5 + 7^5 - 9^4}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$10280 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{19} - 8^1 + 0^1}{1^0 + 0^0 - 2^4 + 8^2 + 0^0}$$

$$10282 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^7 + 8^5 - 2^{11}}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10283 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{19} + 8^2 + 3^4}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^5 + 8^1 + 3^2}$$

$$10285 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^9 + 8^3 + 5^9}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 8^2 + 5^3}$$

$$10286 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 2^{14} + 8^7 - 6^8}{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 6^2}$$

$$10287 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 2^{19} + 8^1 + 7^3}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 7^2}$$

$$10289 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 2^{17} + 8^6 - 9^5}{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$10292 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{13} - 9^5 + 2^{19}}{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^2 + 9^1 + 2^5}$$

$$10293 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 2^{10} - 9^4 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10294 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 2^5 + 9^7 + 4^8}{-1^0 + 0^0 - 2^1 + 9^3 - 4^4}$$

$$10295 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{20} + 9^5 - 5^7}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^4 + 9^2 + 5^0}$$

$$10296 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{12} + 9^3 + 6^6}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10297 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 2^9 + 9^3 + 7^7}{-1^0 + 0^0 - 2^1 + 9^2 + 7^0}$$

$$10298 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{17} - 9^5 + 8^2}{1^0 + 0^1 + 2^2 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10299 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^{12} + 9^1 + 9^6}{1^0 + 0^0 + 2^5 + 9^1 + 9^1}$$

$$10308 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^{16} + 0^0 - 8^3}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^4 + 0^0 + 8^4}$$

$$10322 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^4 + 2^{11} + 2^{13}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10323 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 3^0 + 2^{19} + 3^7}{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 2^5 + 3^2}$$

$$10324 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 3^6 - 2^{16} + 4^{13}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^8 - 2^0 - 4^3}$$

$$10325 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 2^{17} + 5^5}{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^2 + 2^0 + 5^0}$$

$$10326 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 3^7 + 2^{17} + 6^6}{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 2^3 + 6^1}$$

$$10327 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 3^{10} + 2^9 + 7^4}{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$10328 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 3^{10} - 2^{10} + 8^6}{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^3 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10332 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^6 + 3^{14} + 2^4}{-1^0 + 0^1 - 3^2 + 3^6 - 2^8}$$

$$10333 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^6 + 3^8 + 3^{13}}{1^0 + 0^0 - 3^2 + 3^4 + 3^4}$$

$$10334 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 3^6 + 3^9 + 4^4}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 3^0 + 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$10335 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 3^4 + 3^7 + 5^8}{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 3^2 + 5^2}$$

$$10336 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^7 - 3^{10} + 6^8}{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^4 + 3^4 - 6^1}$$

$$10337 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 3^9 + 3^{13} + 7^7}{-1^0 + 0^1 - 3^1 + 3^5 - 7^1}$$

$$10338 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^4 + 3^8 + 8^6}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 3^2 + 3^2 + 8^1}$$

$$10342 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^{11} - 4^8 - 2^{13}}{1^1 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 2^1}$$

$$10344 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 3^{12} + 4^3 + 4^{10}}{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^0 - 4^2 + 4^3}$$

$$10345 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 3^8 - 4^{10} + 5^{10}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^6}$$

$$10346 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^{13} + 4^4 - 6^4}{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 6^3}$$

$$10347 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 7^9}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 7^2}$$

$$10348 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^1 - 4^8 + 8^6}{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^0 + 4^2 + 8^0}$$

$$10349 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 9^1}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 3^0 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$10352 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 2^{13}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10353 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 3^2}$$

$$10354 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 5^8 + 4^{10}}{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 4^1}$$

$$10356 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^{10} + 5^5 - 6^2}{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10357 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 3^9 + 5^{10} - 7^1}{-1^0 + 0^0 - 3^3 + 5^4 + 7^3}$$

$$10358 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^{14} + 5^7 - 8^6}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 3^5 + 5^4 + 8^2}$$

$$10359 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 3^2 - 5^5 + 9^6}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 9^2}$$

$$10362 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^9 + 6^4 - 2^8}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$10363 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 3^4 + 6^8 - 3^6}{-1^0 + 0^0 - 3^3 + 6^3 - 3^3}$$

$$10364 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 3^{10} - 6^3 + 4^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 4^0}$$

$$10365 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 3^4 + 6^7 + 5^0}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 5^2}$$

$$10367 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^0}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^3 + 6^0 + 7^0}$$

$$10368 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^0 + 6^7 + 8^0}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^0 + 6^2 - 8^1}$$

$$10369 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 9^0}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^3 + 6^0 + 9^0}$$

$$10372 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 3^7 - 7^1 + 2^{13}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10374 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 3^5 + 7^6 - 4^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$10375 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^{11} - 7^6 + 5^{10}}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 3^6 + 7^3 - 5^3}$$

$$10376 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 3^7 + 7^4 + 6^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^3 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10378 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^{14} - 7^3 + 8^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 3^0 - 7^2 + 8^3}$$

$$10382 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 8^0 + 2^{20}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^1 + 8^2 + 2^5}$$

$$10383 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^7 - 8^4 + 3^{12}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^3 - 8^0 + 3^3}$$

$$10384 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 8^8 - 4^8}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 3^7 - 8^3 - 4^3}$$

$$10385 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 3^2 + 8^7 + 5^4}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^5 - 8^2 + 5^2}$$

$$10386 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 3^3 + 8^3 + 6^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^0 - 8^1 + 6^2}$$

$$10387 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 3^{14} + 8^6 + 7^7}{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 8^3 + 7^2}$$

$$10388 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 8^5}{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10389 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^0 - 8^5 + 9^6}{1^0 + 0^0 - 3^2 + 8^2 - 9^1}$$

$$10392 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 3^9 + 9^5 - 2^{13}}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10393 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 3^0 + 9^7 - 3^7}{1^0 + 0^1 - 3^3 + 9^3 - 3^5}$$

$$10394 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 3^9 + 9^2 + 4^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 3^0 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$10395 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^{15} + 9^4 + 5^2}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 3^3 + 9^3 + 5^4}$$

$$10396 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 3^3 + 9^3 + 6^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^3 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10397 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 3^7 + 9^1 + 7^7}{1^0 + 0^0 + 3^3 + 9^0 + 7^2}$$

$$10398 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 3^7 - 9^1 + 8^6}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 3^3 - 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10399 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 3^{11} - 9^3 + 9^6}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 3^3 - 9^0 + 9^1}$$

$$10406 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^5 + 0^1 + 6^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^3 + 0^0 - 6^2}$$

$$10423 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 4^1 + 2^7 + 3^{12}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 2^5 + 3^0}$$

$$10425 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 4^9 - 2^{15} - 5^2}{1^0 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$10426 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 4^7 + 2^{17} - 6^0}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 6^1}$$

$$10427 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 4^7 + 2^{17} + 7^1}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 7^1}$$

$$10429 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^{12} + 2^{16} + 9^2}{-1^0 + 0^0 - 4^2 + 2^{13} - 9^4}$$

$$10432 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 4^{13} - 3^{16} - 2^{14}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^2 + 3^5 + 2^{11}}$$

$$10434 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 4^7 + 3^{12} + 4^{10}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^3 + 3^3 + 4^3}$$

$$10435 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 4^{10} + 3^{13} - 5^5}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 3^2 + 5^2}$$

$$10436 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 4^9 + 3^{15} - 6^7}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 3^2 + 6^4}$$

$$10437 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^6 - 3^3 + 7^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^1 - 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$10438 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^0 + 3^9 + 8^6}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 3^0 + 8^1}$$

$$10445 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 4^5 + 4^9 + 5^1}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 5^2}$$

$$10450 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 4^5 + 5^9 + 0^1}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^3 + 5^3 + 0^1}$$

$$10453 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 3^{15}}{1^0 + 0^1 - 4^5 + 5^5 - 3^6}$$

$$10454 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 4^9 + 5^{10} - 4^9}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 4^4}$$

$$10456 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 4^3 + 5^{10} + 6^3}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 6^2}$$

$$10458 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 4^{12} - 5^6 + 8^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^2}$$

$$10459 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 4^4 + 5^8 + 9^4}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 9^1}$$

$$10463 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^9 - 6^4 + 3^6}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 3^0}$$

$$10464 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 4^4 + 6^6 + 4^7}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$10465 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^8 + 6^7 - 5^3}{1^0 + 0^1 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 5^2}$$

$$10467 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^8 - 6^3 + 7^8}{1^0 + 0^0 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^3}$$

$$10468 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 4^{11} + 6^{10} + 8^4}{-1^0 + 0^0 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^4}$$

$$10472 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^0 - 7^3 + 2^{18}}{1^0 + 0^1 + 4^0 + 7^1 + 2^4}$$

$$10473 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 4^8 + 7^1 + 3^{16}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^6 + 7^0 + 3^2}$$

$$10474 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 4^4 + 7^6 - 4^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$10476 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 4^6 + 7^7 - 6^2}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 6^1}$$

$$10477 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^6 + 7^2 + 7^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^1 - 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$10478 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 7^7 + 8^7}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^1 + 7^3 - 8^2}$$

$$10482 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 4^3 + 8^6 - 2^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 8^1 + 2^4}$$

$$10483 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^8 + 8^7 + 3^{12}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^1 + 8^1 + 3^5}$$

$$10485 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^1 + 8^6 - 5^2}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 5^2}$$

$$10486 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 8^6 + 6^0}{1^0 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 8^0 + 6^1}$$

$$10487 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 4^2 + 8^6 + 7^2}{1^0 + 0^1 + 4^2 + 8^0 + 7^1}$$

$$10488 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 4^3 - 8^1 + 8^6}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 8^0 + 8^1}$$

$$10489 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 4^0 + 8^6 + 9^2}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^0}$$

$$10493 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 4^7 + 9^6 - 3^7}{1^0 + 0^0 - 4^1 + 9^2 - 3^3}$$

$$10496 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 4^8 + 9^6 + 6^4}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 4^2 + 9^2 - 6^1}$$

$$10497 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 4^4 + 9^5 - 7^5}{1^0 + 0^1 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$10499 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 4^3 - 9^5 + 9^6}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 4^3 - 9^1 - 9^1}$$

$$10502 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 5^8 - 0^0 - 2^{11}}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 0^1 + 2^5}$$

$$10522 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 5^9 - 2^7 + 2^{12}}{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^2 + 2^5 + 2^7}$$

$$10523 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^6 + 2^7 + 3^{12}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 2^4 + 3^2}$$

$$10525 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 5^1 - 2^{15} + 5^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 2^1 + 5^2}$$

$$10526 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 5^3 - 2^{14} + 6^8}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 5^3 - 2^0 + 6^2}$$

$$10527 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 2^{16} - 7^4}{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$10528 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 5^8 - 2^{10} - 8^2}{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 2^1 + 8^1}$$

$$10531 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 5^9 - 3^{12} + 1^0}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 5^3 + 3^2 + 1^0}$$

$$10532 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 5^3 + 3^8 + 2^{12}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10533 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 5^7 - 3^5 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 3^2}$$

$$10534 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 5^3 + 3^8 + 4^6}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$10536 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 5^5 + 3^9 + 6^6}{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 3^1 + 6^0}$$

$$10538 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^9 - 3^{13} - 8^3}{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 3^3 + 8^0}$$

$$10542 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^7 - 4^8 - 2^{11}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 5^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10543 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^{13} + 4^{11} - 3^{19}}{1^0 + 0^1 - 5^4 + 4^1 + 3^8}$$

$$10545 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 5^6 + 4^{10} + 5^8}{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 4^1 + 5^3}$$

$$10546 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 5^{10} - 4^3 + 6^2}{-1^0 + 0^1 - 5^4 + 4^4 + 6^4}$$

$$10548 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 5^8 + 4^8 + 8^7}{1^0 + 0^1 - 5^2 + 4^4 - 8^2}$$

$$10552 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 5^4 - 5^6 + 2^{17}}{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 2^3}$$

$$10553 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 5^9 - 3^{13}}{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 5^1 + 3^3}$$

$$10554 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 5^3 + 5^8 - 4^1}{-1^0 + 0^1 - 5^0 - 5^2 + 4^3}$$

$$10556 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 5^6 + 6^7}{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 5^2 + 6^0}$$

$$10557 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 5^5 - 5^5 + 7^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$10558 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 5^5 + 5^7 - 8^5}{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10559 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 5^2 + 5^8 + 9^2}{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 5^2 + 9^1}$$

$$10562 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 5^0 + 6^8 - 2^8}{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 6^0 + 2^5}$$

$$10563 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 5^8 - 6^2 + 3^5}{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 3^2}$$

$$10564 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 5^1 + 6^8 + 4^3}{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 6^3 - 4^3}$$

$$10566 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 6^7 + 6^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 5^2 - 6^1 + 6^2}$$

$$10569 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^3 + 6^8 + 9^3}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 5^2 + 6^3 - 9^2}$$

$$10572 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 5^2 - 7^5 + 2^{19}}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 5^0 + 7^2 + 2^1}$$

$$10573 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 - 7^6 + 3^{15}}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 5^4 - 7^1 + 3^6}$$

$$10575 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 + 5^6}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$10576 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 6^6}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 6^1}$$

$$10578 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^4}{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10579 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 7^8 + 9^3}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 5^4 + 7^0 - 9^2}$$

$$10582 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 8^5 - 2^{10}}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10583 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 5^6 + 8^5 - 3^8}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10585 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 5^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$10587 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 5^9 - 8^0 + 7^8}{-1^0 + 0^1 - 5^3 + 8^3 + 7^3}$$

$$10592 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 5^8 - 9^4 + 2^{19}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 2^3}$$

$$10594 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^7 + 9^4 + 4^3}{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$10596 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 5^8 + 9^6 - 6^3}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 9^2 + 6^0}$$

$$10597 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 5^2 - 9^1 + 7^8}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 5^4 - 9^2 + 7^0}$$

$$10622 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^9 - 2^{10} + 2^{17}}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 - 2^6 + 2^{10}}$$

$$10623 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 6^2 + 2^{12} + 3^8}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10624 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^6 - 2^6 - 4^6}{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$10625 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^7 + 2^6 - 5^7}{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$10626 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 6^5 - 2^{17} + 6^8}{-1^0 + 0^1 - 6^1 - 2^6 + 6^3}$$

$$10627 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^2 + 2^{13} + 7^4}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 7^0}$$

$$10629 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^1 + 2^0 + 9^6}{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 2^2 + 9^1}$$

$$10632 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 6^2 + 3^{13} + 2^9}{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 3^4 + 2^5}$$

$$10633 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 6^2 + 3^5 + 3^{12}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^2 + 3^1 + 3^2}$$

$$10634 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 3^{12} + 4^4}{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 3^3 + 4^2}$$

$$10635 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 6^5 + 3^2 + 5^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^1 + 3^1 + 5^2}$$

$$10636 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 6^2 + 3^8 + 6^6}{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10637 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^9 + 3^2 + 7^5}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 6^4 - 3^1 - 7^3}$$

$$10638 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 6^7 - 3^{12} + 8^6}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10639 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 6^{11} + 3^{10} + 9^9}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^3 + 3^7 - 9^2}$$

$$10640 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^6 - 4^6 + 0^1}{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 0^1}$$

$$10642 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^6 - 4^6 + 2^3}{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10643 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^6 - 4^1 + 3^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10644 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 4^2 - 4^6}{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$10645 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^5 - 4^4 + 5^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$10646 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^5 + 4^7 + 6^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10648 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^6 + 4^9 - 8^1}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^2 + 4^0 - 8^1}$$

$$10649 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^7 + 4^5 + 9^4}{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 4^2 + 9^1}$$

$$10653 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^8 + 5^7 + 3^1}{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 5^3 + 3^1}$$

$$10654 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 6^0 + 5^{10} + 4^6}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^2 + 5^4 + 4^4}$$

$$10656 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 5^0 + 6^7}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 5^2 + 6^0}$$

$$10657 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 6^6 + 5^8 - 7^3}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 6^0 - 5^1 + 7^2}$$

$$10659 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 6^7 + 5^8 + 9^4}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 9^1}$$

$$10667 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^3 + 6^9 + 7^4}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 6^1 + 6^4 - 7^3}$$

$$10672 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 7^6 - 2^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 2^0}$$

$$10673 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 6^0 + 7^6 - 3^5}{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 3^0}$$

$$10675 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 6^5 + 7^6 - 5^5}{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^1 + 7^0 + 5^0}$$

$$10676 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 7^6 - 6^3}{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$10678 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 6^9 + 7^4 - 8^2}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 6^4 - 7^3 - 8^1}$$

$$10679 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^6 + 7^6 + 9^4}{1^0 + 0^0 + 6^1 + 7^1 + 9^0}$$

$$10683 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 8^5 + 3^7}{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10685 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 6^9 + 8^8 - 5^2}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 5^4}$$

$$10687 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^5 + 8^3 + 7^4}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$10688 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 6^8 - 8^5 + 8^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^2 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10689 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 6^1 + 8^6 - 9^5}{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$10692 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 9^4 + 2^{12}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10693 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 + 3^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10694 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 6^2 + 9^4 + 4^6}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$10702 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^7 + 0^0 + 2^9}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 7^2 + 0^1 + 2^7}$$

$$10703 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^6 + 0^0 + 3^4}{1^1 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 0^1 + 3^1}$$

$$10722 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^7 + 2^0 + 2^{11}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 2^2 + 2^6}$$

$$10723 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^3 + 2^{13} + 3^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10724 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 7^4 + 2^{17} + 4^2}{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 2^3 + 4^0}$$

$$10725 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 7^5 - 2^8 + 5^6}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 5^0}$$

$$10726 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^3 - 2^{12} + 6^6}{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10727 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^3 + 2^2 + 7^6}{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 7^1}$$

$$10728 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 7^4 + 2^{17} + 8^2}{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 8^1}$$

$$10729 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 2^{18} + 9^0}{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 2^3 + 9^1}$$

$$10732 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 7^5 + 3^4 + 2^{18}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 3^0 + 2^4}$$

$$10735 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 3^8 + 5^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 3^2 + 5^2}$$

$$10736 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^4 + 3^{12} - 6^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^2 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10742 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^6 + 4^4 + 2^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 4^1 + 2^2}$$

$$10743 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 7^2 - 4^9 + 3^{13}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^2 + 4^3 + 3^2}$$

$$10744 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 7^2 - 4^5 + 4^8}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$10745 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^7 + 4^2 + 5^8}{-1^0 + 0^1 - 7^1 - 4^1 + 5^3}$$

$$10746 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^6 + 4^2 + 6^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 7^0 + 4^1 + 6^2}$$

$$10747 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^4 - 4^5 + 7^9}{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 4^6 - 7^3}$$

$$10748 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 7^4 + 4^{14} + 8^6}{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^5 + 4^6 + 8^4}$$

$$10749 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 7^6 - 4^4 + 9^7}{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^5 - 4^7 + 9^1}$$

$$10752 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 7^6 + 5^4 - 2^1}{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10753 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 7^6 + 5^4 + 3^2}{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 5^1 + 3^1}$$

$$10754 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 5^9 + 4^6}{-1^0 + 0^0 - 7^1 + 5^3 + 4^3}$$

$$10756 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^3 - 5^4 + 6^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 7^1 - 5^0 + 6^2}$$

$$10758 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 7^6 + 5^4 + 8^2}{1^0 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10763 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 7^3 + 6^7 + 3^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^0 + 6^2 - 3^2}$$

$$10764 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^3 - 6^4 + 4^8}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$10765 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 7^2 + 6^7 + 5^0}{1^0 + 0^0 - 7^1 + 6^1 + 5^2}$$

$$10767 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^0 + 6^7 + 7^1}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 7^0 + 6^2 - 7^1}$$

$$10769 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 7^2 + 6^7 + 9^1}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^0 + 6^2 - 9^1}$$

$$10772 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 7^4 + 7^9 - 2^{12}}{-1^0 + 0^0 - 7^1 - 7^3 + 2^{12}}$$

$$10782 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 7^5 + 8^5 + 2^{14}}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10783 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 7^8 + 8^4 + 3^2}{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^2 + 8^3 - 3^3}$$

$$10785 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 7^8 + 8^5 + 5^{10}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^3 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$10792 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^6 + 9^6 - 2^{17}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^0 + 9^2 - 2^5}$$

$$10795 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^7 + 9^0 - 5^5}{1^0 + 0^1 + 7^2 + 9^0 + 5^2}$$

$$10796 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 7^4 + 9^6 - 6^2}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^2 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10797 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^4 + 9^6 + 7^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 7^2}$$

$$10798 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 7^4 + 9^6 + 8^2}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 7^2 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10824 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 8^1 - 2^3 + 4^{12}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 8^3 + 2^4 + 4^5}$$

$$10825 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 8^1 + 2^{18} - 5^7}{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 2^1 + 5^1}$$

$$10826 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^5 - 2^8 - 6^2}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10829 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 8^7 + 2^{19} - 9^6}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 2^7 + 9^0}$$

$$10832 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^7 - 3^8 - 2^4}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 3^0 + 2^7}$$

$$10833 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 3^3 - 3^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10834 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 3^2 - 4^4}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$10835 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^7 - 3^8 + 5^8}{-1^0 + 0^1 - 8^1 + 3^5 - 5^1}$$

$$10836 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 8^5 + 3^{12} - 6^3}{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 3^0 + 6^2}$$

$$10837 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 3^{10} + 7^5}{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 3^1 + 7^0}$$

$$10839 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 3^5 - 9^1}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$10842 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 8^5 + 4^2 - 2^8}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10843 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 4^9 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 3^3}$$

$$10845 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 8^5 - 4^4 + 5^2}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$10846 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 8^4 - 4^5 + 6^5}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10847 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^6 + 4^{11} - 7^6}{1^0 + 0^1 - 8^1 + 4^3 + 7^3}$$

$$10848 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^2 + 4^8 - 8^3}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 8^0 + 4^0 + 8^1}$$

$$10849 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 8^3 + 4^7 + 9^5}{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$10851 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 5^8 + 1^0}{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 5^2 + 1^0}$$

$$10852 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 5^8 - 2^4}{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 2^5}$$

$$10853 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^0 + 5^8 + 3^4}{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 5^2 + 3^0}$$

$$10854 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^6 - 5^4 - 4^5}{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 5^1 + 4^2}$$

$$10855 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^7 + 5^0 - 5^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 8^2 - 5^0 + 5^3}$$

$$10862 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^5 - 6^3 + 2^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10863 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 8^9 + 6^{11} - 3^4}{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 6^4 + 3^9}$$

$$10864 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^0 - 6^6 + 4^{12}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 8^3 + 6^1 + 4^5}$$

$$10865 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^3 + 6^0 + 5^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 6^0 + 5^2}$$

$$10866 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 - 8^3 - 6^5 + 6^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 8^1 - 6^0 + 6^2}$$

$$10867 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^5 - 6^3 + 7^2}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 7^0}$$

$$10869 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^6 - 6^4 + 9^1}{1^1 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$10873 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^7 + 7^0 - 3^{12}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 8^2 + 7^0 + 3^4}$$

$$10874 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^8 + 7^3 + 4^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^3 + 7^1 + 4^5}$$

$$10875 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^{11} - 7^3 + 5^{10}}{1^0 + 0^1 - 8^5 + 7^7 + 5^0}$$

$$10879 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 7^2 - 9^2}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$10882 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 8^1 + 8^5 - 2^7}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10885 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^3 + 8^5 - 5^4}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 5^0}$$

$$10887 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 - 8^3 + 8^6 - 7^3}{1^1 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$10889 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 8^4 + 9^7}{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^1 + 8^3 - 9^2}$$

$$10892 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 8^1 - 9^3 + 2^{18}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 2^4}$$

$$10893 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 9^1 - 3^4}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10894 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 9^2 - 4^1}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$10895 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^5 - 9^2 - 5^0}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$10896 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^5 - 9^2 + 6^0}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10897 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 9^5 + 7^7}{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$10898 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 8^1 - 9^2 + 8^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10899 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 8^5 + 9^1 - 9^2}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$10920 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 - 9^1 + 2^{15} + 0^0}{1^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 0^1}$$

$$10921 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 9^1 + 2^{16} + 1^0}{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 1^0}$$

$$10922 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 9^0 + 2^0 + 2^{15}}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10923 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^{17} + 3^0}{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^3 + 3^0}$$

$$10924 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^{15} + 4^0}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$10925 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^{17} + 5^2}{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^2 + 5^1}$$

$$10926 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 2^{15} + 6^0}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$10927 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^{17} + 7^2}{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 7^1}$$

$$10928 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 8^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10929 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^4 + 2^{16} + 9^5}{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 2^3 + 9^0}$$

$$10932 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 3^3 + 2^{15}}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10933 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 9^4 + 3^7 + 3^7}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10934 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 9^4 + 3^{10} - 4^1}{1^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 4^0}$$

$$10935 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 9^4 + 3^{10} + 5^0}{1^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 5^0}$$

$$10936 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^4 + 3^{10} + 6^1}{1^0 + 0^1 + 9^0 + 3^1 + 6^0}$$

$$10942 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 9^8 - 4^{10} + 2^{13}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 9^0 - 4^4 + 2^{12}}$$

$$10943 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^3 + 4^9 - 3^5}{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 4^1 + 3^2}$$

$$10945 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 4^8 + 5^3}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$10946 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 9^5 + 4^9 + 6^8}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 9^2 + 4^4 - 6^0}$$

$$10948 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 9^2 - 4^1 + 8^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10952 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^2 + 5^1 + 2^{15}}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10953 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 5^9 + 3^{14}}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 9^0 + 5^4 - 3^2}$$

$$10954 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 9^3 + 5^2 + 4^9}{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 5^1 + 4^2}$$

$$10958 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^2 + 5^2 + 8^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10962 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 9^2 + 6^2 + 2^{15}}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10965 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 - 9^7 + 6^9 + 5^7}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^2 - 6^3 + 5^4}$$

$$10967 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 9^2 + 6^7 - 7^5}{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 6^1 + 7^1}$$

$$10968 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 9^2 + 6^3 + 8^5}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 8^0}$$

$$10972 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^6 - 7^2 + 2^{20}}{-1^0 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 2^7}$$

$$10973 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 9^3 + 7^5 - 3^8}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 9^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$10975 := \frac{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^6 + 7^1 - 5^6}{-1^0 - 0^0 - 9^0 + 7^2 + 5^0}$$

$$10982 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 9^7 - 8^3 - 2^{20}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^2 + 8^0 + 2^8}$$

$$10984 := \frac{-1^0 + 0^1 + 9^3 + 8^7 + 4^3}{-1^0 - 0^0 + 9^0 - 8^2 + 4^4}$$

$$10986 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 + 9^3 + 8^3 + 6^8}{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^2 + 8^2 + 6^1}$$

$$10989 := \frac{1^0 + 0^1 - 9^1 - 8^4 + 9^5}{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$10992 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 9^1 + 9^5 - 2^{12}}{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$10997 := \frac{-1^0 - 0^0 + 9^3 + 9^7 - 7^0}{1^0 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 9^2 + 7^3}$$

$$11029 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 0^0 - 2^{11} + 9^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 0^0 - 2^5 + 9^2}$$

$$11152 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 1^0 + 5^7 - 2^6}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 2^0}$$

$$11156 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 1^0 + 5^7 - 6^2}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 6^0}$$

$$11159 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 1^0 + 5^7 - 9^1}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 9^1}$$

$$11222 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 2^7 + 2^{10} + 2^{15}}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$$

$$11223 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 2^{12} + 2^{18} + 3^4}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 2^4 + 3^1}$$

$$11225 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 2^6 + 2^9 + 5^7}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$11229 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 2^1 + 2^{17} + 9^6}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^4 + 2^5 + 9^1}$$

$$11233 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^5 + 3^6 + 3^{13}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 3^4}$$

$$11235 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 2^9 + 3^{11} + 5^5}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^2 + 3^2 + 5^0}$$

$$11239 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^{11} - 3^9 + 9^7}{1^0 + 1^0 - 2^6 - 3^5 + 9^3}$$

$$11242 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 2^6 + 4^5 + 2^{15}}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 2^0}$$

$$11243 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^6 + 4^{11} - 3^6}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^6 + 4^3 + 3^5}$$

$$11245 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 2^1 + 4^9 + 5^9}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^3 + 4^3 + 5^3}$$

$$11246 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^{17} + 4^6 - 6^3}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^3 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$11247 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 2^{15} + 4^5 - 7^2}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 7^0}$$

$$11249 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 2^{19} + 4^6 + 9^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 9^0}$$

$$11253 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 2^{16} + 5^{10} - 3^0}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 2^2 + 5^4 + 3^5}$$

$$11257 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^9 + 5^9 + 7^6}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^3 + 5^3 + 7^2}$$

$$11259 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^{18} + 5^9 + 9^5}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 2^1 + 5^3 + 9^2}$$

$$11262 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^{10} - 6^1 + 2^{15}}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$11263 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^{18} - 6^2 + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^2 + 6^1 + 3^3}$$

$$11264 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 2^8 + 6^8 - 4^{10}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 6^2 + 4^2}$$

$$11265 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^9 + 6^3 + 5^7}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 5^1}$$

$$11268 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^9 + 6^5 + 8^6}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^3 + 6^1 + 8^1}$$

$$11269 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 2^{19} + 6^9 + 9^5}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^7 - 6^1 + 9^3}$$

$$11273 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^{12} + 7^7 + 3^8}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^6 + 7^1 + 3^0}$$

$$11283 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 2^0 + 8^6 - 3^{10}}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 8^1 + 3^2}$$

$$11285 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^{17} + 8^1 + 5^6}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 8^1 + 5^0}$$

$$11286 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^{11} + 8^7 - 6^1}{1^0 + 1^0 + 2^5 - 8^2 + 6^3}$$

$$11287 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 2^{19} + 8^7 + 7^8}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 2^{10} + 8^2 - 7^3}$$

$$11289 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 2^1 + 8^7 + 9^5}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 2^7 + 8^2 + 9^0}$$

$$11295 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 2^5 - 9^4 + 5^8}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 2^1 + 9^1 + 5^2}$$

$$11299 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 2^{18} - 9^4 + 9^8}{1^0 + 1^0 - 2^{11} - 9^3 + 9^4}$$

$$11316 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 3^{15} - 1^0 - 6^3}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 3^3 + 1^0 + 6^4}$$

$$11325 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 3^9 - 2^{13} + 5^9}{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^3 + 2^4 + 5^3}$$

$$11326 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 3^{10} + 2^{16} + 6^0}{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 6^1}$$

$$11327 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 3^3 + 2^{16} + 7^4}{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$11329 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 3^4 - 2^{11} + 9^7}{-1^0 + 1^0 - 3^2 + 2^9 - 9^2}$$

$$11332 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^{10} + 3^{12} + 2^{15}}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 3^3 + 3^3 + 2^0}$$

$$11334 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 3^1 + 3^{14} - 4^2}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 3^5 + 3^5 - 4^3}$$

$$11337 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 3^{11} + 3^{13} - 7^2}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 3^1 + 3^4 + 7^2}$$

$$11342 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 3^{15} + 4^0 - 2^{18}}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 2^9}$$

$$11343 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 3^2}$$

$$11345 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 3^4 + 4^9 + 5^7}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 5^2}$$

$$11347 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 3^4 - 4^6 + 7^6}{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 7^0}$$

$$11349 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 3^1 - 4^7 + 9^7}{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^4 + 4^4 + 9^2}$$

$$11352 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^{12} + 5^5 - 2^{10}}{1^0 + 1^0 - 3^4 + 5^3 + 2^0}$$

$$11354 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 3^8 + 5^9 - 4^7}{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^3 + 5^3 + 4^2}$$

$$11356 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^{13} - 5^8 + 6^2}{1^0 + 1^0 - 3^3 + 5^3 + 6^1}$$

$$11362 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^{15} + 6^4 + 2^0}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 3^0 + 6^4 - 2^5}$$

$$11365 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 3^{16} + 6^{10} + 5^{10}}{1^0 + 1^0 - 3^6 - 6^1 + 5^5}$$

$$11367 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 3^{11} + 6^7 - 7^4}{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$11369 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 3^8 + 6^{15} + 9^8}{-1^0 + 1^0 - 3^8 - 6^8 + 9^8}$$

$$11372 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 3^5 - 7^3 + 2^{18}}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 3^3 - 7^0 - 2^0}$$

$$11373 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 3^7 + 7^0 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$11376 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 3^2 + 7^7 + 6^7}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 3^5 + 7^3 - 6^0}$$

$$11378 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 3^6 - 7^7 + 8^7}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 3^0 + 7^2 + 8^2}$$

$$11384 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 3^{11} - 8^0 + 4^7}{1^1 + 1^1 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 4^1}$$

$$11385 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 3^7 + 8^7 - 5^3}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 3^1 + 8^2 + 5^3}$$

$$11392 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 3^6 + 9^5 + 2^{16}}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 9^1 + 2^0}$$

$$11394 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^9 + 9^5 + 4^5}{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^1 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$11395 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 3^3 - 9^2 + 5^{10}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 9^3 + 5^3}$$

$$11397 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 3^{12} + 9^6 - 7^7}{1^1 + 1^1 + 3^1 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$11398 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 9^1 + 8^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 3^3 - 9^0 - 8^0}$$

$$11423 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 4^5 - 2^{14} + 3^{12}}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 4^1 + 2^4 + 3^3}$$

$$11425 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 2^{18} + 5^4}{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 2^4 + 5^0}$$

$$11426 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^8 - 2^{13} - 6^3}{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$11429 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 4^1 + 2^{18} + 9^3}{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 2^3 + 9^1}$$

$$11433 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^7 - 3^4 + 3^8}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 4^1 - 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$11435 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 4^3 + 3^9 + 5^5}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 4^1 - 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$11437 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 4^1 - 3^4 + 7^7}{-1^0 + 1^0 - 4^1 + 3^3 + 7^2}$$

$$11442 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 4^1 + 4^5 + 2^{18}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 4^1 + 2^4}$$

$$11453 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 4^2 + 5^9 + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 1^0 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 3^5}$$

$$11457 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^8 + 5^3 + 7^6}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 5^1 + 7^1}$$

$$11459 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 9^4}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 4^1 - 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$11462 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^8 - 6^2 - 2^{13}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$11463 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^6 + 6^6 + 3^8}{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$11465 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 4^2 + 6^4 + 5^{11}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 5^3}$$

$$11473 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^9 + 7^2 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 3^2}$$

$$11482 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^8 + 8^2 - 2^{13}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$11483 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 4^7 + 8^0 + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 8^1 + 3^1}$$

$$11485 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 4^{10} + 8^2 + 5^{10}}{-1^0 + 1^0 - 4^7 + 8^5 - 5^6}$$

$$11487 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 4^6 + 8^5 - 7^4}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$11495 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 4^8 + 9^4 - 5^5}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$11497 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 4^7 + 9^4 + 7^2}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 4^1 - 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$11523 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 2^{12} + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 2^2 + 3^2}$$

$$11526 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^6 - 2^{12} - 6^0}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$11527 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 5^9 + 2^6 - 7^7}{1^0 + 1^0 + 5^2 + 2^6 + 7^1}$$

$$11528 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^6 + 2^0 - 8^4}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 8^0}$$

$$11529 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^8 + 2^8 + 9^6}{1^0 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 2^6 + 9^1}$$

$$11532 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 3^0 - 2^{12}}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$11534 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 3^1 - 4^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$11535 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 5^3 + 3^{13} + 5^7}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 5^1 + 3^3 + 5^3}$$

$$11536 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^{10} + 3^6 - 6^8}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 5^2 + 3^6 - 6^0}$$

$$11538 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 3^2 - 8^4}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$11539 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 5^4 - 3^6 + 9^5}{1^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$11543 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 5^9 - 4^5 - 3^{10}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 5^3 + 4^3 - 3^3}$$

$$11545 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 4^{10} + 5^9}{1^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 4^4 + 5^0}$$

$$11549 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 5^3 - 4^3 + 9^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 5^2 + 4^3 + 9^1}$$

$$11552 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^2 + 5^6 - 2^{12}}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$11554 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 5^2 + 5^6 - 4^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$11557 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 5^9 + 7^0}{-1^0 + 1^0 - 5^1 + 5^3 + 7^2}$$

$$11562 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 5^5 + 6^8 + 2^0}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 5^1 + 6^3 - 2^6}$$

$$11572 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^9 - 7^7 - 2^{20}}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 7^1 + 2^0}$$

$$11573 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^6 - 7^5 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$11574 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 7^1 + 4^9}{1^0 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 7^0 + 4^2}$$

$$11578 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 5^6 + 7^2 - 8^4}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 8^0}$$

$$11587 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^{11} - 8^3 + 7^1}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 5^3 + 8^4 - 7^1}$$

$$11589 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 5^4 + 8^6 - 9^4}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 9^1}$$

$$11592 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^8 + 9^6 + 2^{20}}{-1^0 + 1^0 - 5^1 - 9^2 + 2^8}$$

$$11594 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 5^6 - 9^0 + 4^8}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 5^0 + 9^1 + 4^0}$$

$$11603 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^6 + 0^0 - 3^5}{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 0^1 + 3^0}$$

$$11622 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^7 + 2^4 - 2^{10}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^1 + 2^3 + 2^3}$$

$$11623 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^4 - 2^{12} + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^1 + 2^2 + 3^1}$$

$$11624 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^7 + 2^6 - 4^5}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 4^2}$$

$$11625 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^3 + 2^{16} + 5^6}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 5^1}$$

$$11626 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 6^3 + 2^6 + 6^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 6^0 + 2^0 + 6^1}$$

$$11627 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^8 + 2^{18} - 7^2}{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^2 + 2^7 + 7^0}$$

$$11629 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 6^5 - 2^{14} + 9^5}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 9^0}$$

$$11635 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^7 + 3^{11} + 5^7}{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^2 + 3^1 + 5^1}$$

$$11637 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^5 + 3^{16} + 7^4}{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^4 + 3^0 + 7^4}$$

$$11642 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^7 - 4^2 - 2^9}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 + 4^1 + 2^4}$$

$$11643 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^6 - 4^0 - 3^4}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^0 + 4^1 + 3^0}$$

$$11644 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 - 4^2 - 4^3}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 4^1}$$

$$11645 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 6^1 + 4^{12} - 5^9}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^4 + 4^1 - 5^2}$$

$$11646 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 6^1 - 4^3 + 6^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 6^0 + 4^0 + 6^1}$$

$$11647 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 6^0 + 4^{10} - 7^3}{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 - 4^4 + 7^3}$$

$$11653 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 - 5^3 + 3^4}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 - 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$11657 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^6 - 5^2 - 7^0}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 - 5^0 + 7^0}$$

$$11658 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 - 5^2 + 8^0}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 6^0 - 5^0 + 8^1}$$

$$11659 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^5 + 5^6 - 9^2}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 - 5^0 - 9^0}$$

$$11662 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 6^1 + 6^6 - 2^1}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$11663 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 6^0 + 6^6 - 3^0}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 6^0 + 6^1 + 3^0}$$

$$11664 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 4^0}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$11665 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 6^6 + 5^0}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 6^0 + 6^1 + 5^0}$$

$$11668 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^1 + 6^6 + 8^1}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 6^0 - 6^0 + 8^1}$$

$$11673 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 7^1 + 3^3}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 - 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$11675 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^5 - 7^2 + 5^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 - 7^0 - 5^0}$$

$$11676 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^0 + 7^2 + 6^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 6^0 + 7^0 + 6^1}$$

$$11677 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 7^0 + 7^2}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 - 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$11679 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^1}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 - 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$11680 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 0^1}{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 0^1}$$

$$11682 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 8^1 + 2^6}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 2^1}$$

$$11683 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 + 8^6 + 3^8}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 6^0 - 8^0 + 3^3}$$

$$11684 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 8^2 + 4^2}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 4^1}$$

$$11687 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 6^6 + 8^6 - 7^5}{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 7^0}$$

$$11688 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 6^7 + 8^2 + 8^3}{1^1 + 1^1 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 8^1}$$

$$11695 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^5 - 9^1 + 5^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 - 9^0 - 5^0}$$

$$11697 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^6 + 9^2 + 7^2}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 6^1 - 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$11722 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 7^4 - 2^0 + 2^{15}}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$$

$$11723 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 3^{13}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^2 + 2^2 + 3^4}$$

$$11724 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 2^{15} + 4^0}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$11725 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^6 - 2^{10} + 5^4}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 2^1 + 5^1}$$

$$11729 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 7^4 + 2^6 + 9^7}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^3 - 2^4 + 9^2}$$

$$11732 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 3^3 + 2^{15}}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$11733 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^3 - 3^6 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$11734 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^6 - 3^9 - 4^6}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 4^1}$$

$$11736 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 7^6 + 3^0 + 6^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 7^0 + 3^2 + 6^1}$$

$$11738 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^6 + 3^5 - 8^3}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 8^1}$$

$$11739 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 7^3 - 3^2 + 9^5}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$11743 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 7^1 + 4^9 + 3^9}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 - 4^1 + 3^3}$$

$$11752 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 7^6 + 5^0 - 2^7}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 5^1 + 2^1}$$

$$11753 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 7^2 + 5^6 + 3^9}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 3^0}$$

$$11754 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^6 - 5^3 + 4^2}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 5^1 + 4^1}$$

$$11756 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^3 + 5^2 + 6^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 7^0 + 5^0 + 6^1}$$

$$11758 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^5 + 5^8 + 8^4}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^1 + 5^2 + 8^0}$$

$$11761 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 7^6 - 6^2 - 1^0}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 1^0}$$

$$11762 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^6 + 6^0 - 2^5}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 2^0}$$

$$11763 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^6 + 6^1 - 3^3}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 3^0}$$

$$11764 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 7^6 - 6^1 - 4^0}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 4^0}$$

$$11765 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^6 - 6^1 + 5^1}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 6^1 + 5^0}$$

$$11768 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^7 + 6^3 + 8^0}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 7^1 + 6^0 + 8^2}$$

$$11770 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^2 + 7^6 + 0^1}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 7^1 + 0^1}$$

$$11772 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^1 + 7^6 + 2^6}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 7^0 + 2^3}$$

$$11782 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 7^9 + 8^0 - 2^8}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 2^9}$$

$$11783 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^6 - 8^2 + 3^5}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 3^0}$$

$$11789 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 7^5 - 8^2 + 9^8}{1^0 + 1^0 - 7^4 - 8^3 + 9^4}$$

$$11792 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 7^3 + 9^5 + 2^8}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$11793 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 7^0 - 9^2 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$11794 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 7^1 - 9^4 + 4^8}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 4^0}$$

$$11795 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 7^2 + 9^5 - 5^2}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$11798 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 7^1 + 9^5 - 8^2}{1^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$11809 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 8^0 - 0^0 + 9^5}{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 9^0}$$

$$11822 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 8^1 - 2^{10} + 2^{17}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 2^2 + 2^2}$$

$$11823 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^3 + 2^{15} + 3^7}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$11824 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 8^2 + 2^{19} - 4^6}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 2^5 + 4^1}$$

$$11825 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 8^1 - 2^{18} + 5^9}{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 2^3 + 5^3}$$

$$11826 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 8^7 - 2^{19} - 6^1}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 2^7 + 6^1}$$

$$11829 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 8^2 + 2^5 + 9^5}{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 + 9^0}$$

$$11833 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 8^8 - 3^5 + 3^{16}}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^1 + 3^3 + 3^7}$$

$$11835 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 3^{10} + 5^3}{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$11837 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 8^1 + 3^6 + 7^6}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$11839 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 8^8 - 3^{15} + 9^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^1 + 3^5 + 9^0}$$

$$11843 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^3 - 4^2 + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 4^1 + 3^0}$$

$$11845 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^6 - 4^4 + 5^9}{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^2 - 4^1 + 5^3}$$

$$11853 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^5 - 5^6 + 3^8}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^1 - 5^0 - 3^1}$$

$$11862 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 8^1 + 6^5 + 2^{12}}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$11863 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 3^2}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$11864 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 8^1 + 6^5 + 4^6}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$11865 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 5^1}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 5^0}$$

$$11866 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 8^4 - 6^1 + 6^5}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$11867 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 7^1}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 7^0}$$

$$11869 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 6^5 - 9^0}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 9^0}$$

$$11873 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 8^5 - 7^1 + 3^{12}}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 8^1 + 7^1 + 3^3}$$

$$11876 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 8^4 + 7^7 - 6^0}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^2 + 7^0 + 6^1}$$

$$11879 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 7^3 + 9^5}{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$11892 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^0 + 9^6 - 2^{13}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 9^1 + 2^5}$$

$$11893 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^4 + 9^1 + 3^9}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^1 - 9^0 - 3^1}$$

$$11896 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 8^6 + 9^5 + 6^0}{-1^0 - 1^0 - 8^1 + 9^0 + 6^2}$$

$$11912 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 9^5 + 1^0 + 2^9}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 2^0}$$

$$11922 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 9^5 + 2^0 + 2^{20}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 2^6}$$

$$11923 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 9^2 + 2^{18} + 3^4}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 2^4 + 3^1}$$

$$11925 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 - 9^4 - 2^4 + 5^7}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$11927 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^5 + 2^2 + 7^7}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 2^6 + 7^1}$$

$$11929 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 9^4 - 2^1 + 9^6}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 2^5 + 9^1}$$

$$11932 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 - 9^1 + 3^6 + 2^{19}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 3^2 + 2^5}$$

$$11935 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 3^{10} + 5^4}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$11936 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 9^1 + 3^{14} - 6^8}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^1 + 3^5 + 6^1}$$

$$11937 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^2 + 3^3 + 7^7}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^1 + 3^2 + 7^2}$$

$$11939 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 9^2 + 3^6 + 9^5}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$11943 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 3^{15}}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 9^3 - 4^4 + 3^6}$$

$$11945 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 9^6 - 4^1 + 5^9}{-1^0 - 1^0 + 9^2 + 4^1 + 5^3}$$

$$11952 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^4 + 5^7 - 2^{10}}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 5^1 + 2^0}$$

$$11953 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 5^{10} - 3^3}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^2 + 5^1 + 3^6}$$

$$11954 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 - 9^5 + 5^3 + 4^9}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^1 + 5^1 + 4^0}$$

$$11972 := \frac{-1^0 - 1^0 + 9^2 + 7^4 + 2^{19}}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^1 + 7^0 + 2^5}$$

$$11975 := \frac{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^6 + 7^1 + 5^8}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 7^2 + 5^2}$$

$$11982 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 9^3 + 8^0 + 2^{17}}{-1^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 8^1 + 2^1}$$

$$11985 := \frac{-1^0 + 1^0 + 9^6 - 8^4 - 5^1}{1^0 + 1^0 + 9^1 + 8^1 + 5^2}$$

$$12022 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{13} - 0^0 - 2^{17} + 2^{20}}{1^0 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 2^3 + 2^6}$$

$$12023 := \frac{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 2^{14} + 3^9}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$12025 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{18} + 0^0 + 2^{20} + 5^1}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 - 2^4 + 5^3}$$

$$12026 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 0^0 + 2^{19} - 6^7}{1^0 + 2^1 + 0^0 + 2^4 + 6^0}$$

$$12027 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^5 + 0^1 + 2^{13} + 7^8}{1^0 + 2^3 + 0^1 + 2^7 + 7^3}$$

$$12032 := \frac{1^0 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 3^{11} - 2^{15}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 3^0 + 2^3}$$

$$12034 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{15} + 0^1 - 3^6 + 4^9}{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 3^0 + 4^2}$$

$$12035 := \frac{1^0 - 2^5 + 0^1 + 3^8 + 5^8}{1^0 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 5^2}$$

$$12036 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{17} + 0^1 + 3^3 + 6^4}{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 3^1 + 6^1}$$

$$12037 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{19} + 0^0 - 3^5 + 7^9}{-1^0 + 2^{10} - 0^0 - 3^3 + 7^4}$$

$$12043 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{12} - 0^0 + 4^7 - 3^5}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 0^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$12045 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^7 - 0^0 - 4^8 + 5^8}{1^0 + 2^2 + 0^0 + 4^2 + 5^1}$$

$$12046 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^3 - 0^0 + 4^9 + 6^7}{1^0 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 6^2}$$

$$12047 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^3 - 0^0 - 4^7 + 7^7}{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 4^2 + 7^2}$$

$$12049 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{12} + 0^1 + 4^8 + 9^5}{1^0 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$12053 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{20} + 0^1 + 5^2 + 3^2}{1^0 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 3^4}$$

$$12054 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 - 0^0 + 5^3 + 4^{10}}{1^0 + 2^4 + 0^0 + 5^1 + 4^3}$$

$$12055 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{20} + 0^1 - 5^1 + 5^9}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 0^0 + 5^3 + 5^3}$$

$$12056 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{17} + 0^1 - 5^2 - 6^6}{1^0 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12057 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{17} + 0^1 + 5^0 + 7^8}{-1^0 - 2^7 + 0^1 + 5^4 - 7^1}$$

$$12058 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^3 + 0^1 + 5^5 + 8^6}{1^0 + 2^3 + 0^1 + 5^1 + 8^1}$$

$$12059 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 + 0^0 + 5^9 - 9^2}{-1^0 + 2^7 + 0^0 + 5^2 + 9^1}$$

$$12062 := \frac{1^0 + 2^4 + 0^0 - 6^6 + 2^{17}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 6^0 + 2^2}$$

$$12063 := \frac{1^0 - 2^5 + 0^0 + 6^4 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$12064 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^5 + 0^0 + 6^5 + 4^7}{-1^0 - 2^0 - 0^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$12065 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^8 + 0^0 + 6^5 + 5^8}{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 6^1 + 5^2}$$

$$12067 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{14} + 0^0 - 6^4 + 7^6}{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 7^1}$$

$$12069 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 6^4 + 9^5}{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12072 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{10} + 0^1 + 7^6 + 2^{11}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 2^0}$$

$$12073 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{16} - 0^0 + 7^3 + 3^8}{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 3^1}$$

$$12075 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 0^1 - 7^3 + 5^8}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 7^1 + 5^2}$$

$$12076 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{16} + 0^1 + 7^5 + 6^7}{1^0 + 2^4 + 0^1 + 7^1 + 6^1}$$

$$12077 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{15} + 0^1 - 7^3 + 7^6}{1^0 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$12078 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^7 + 0^1 + 7^8 + 8^5}{1^0 + 2^7 + 0^1 + 7^3 + 8^1}$$

$$12079 := \frac{1^0 + 2^5 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 9^6}{1^0 + 2^5 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 9^1}$$

$$12082 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{11} - 0^0 + 8^3 + 2^{20}}{-1^0 + 2^3 + 0^1 + 8^2 + 2^4}$$

$$12083 := \frac{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 8^4 + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 2^1 + 0^0 + 8^1 + 3^1}$$

$$12089 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{17} + 0^1 + 8^3 - 9^5}{1^0 + 2^1 + 0^0 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12092 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{15} + 0^1 - 9^2 + 2^{20}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 0^1 + 9^2 + 2^0}$$

$$12093 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{17} + 0^1 + 9^0 + 3^{13}}{-1^0 + 2^5 + 0^1 + 9^1 + 3^4}$$

$$12094 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{19} + 0^1 + 9^4 + 4^{11}}{1^0 + 2^3 + 0^1 - 9^3 + 4^5}$$

$$12095 := \frac{1^0 + 2^2 + 0^0 - 9^8 + 5^{11}}{-1^0 - 2^6 - 0^0 - 9^2 + 5^4}$$

$$12096 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^9 + 0^1 + 9^6 + 6^4}{1^0 + 2^5 + 0^0 + 9^1 + 6^0}$$

$$12099 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{10} + 0^1 + 9^4 + 9^4}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 0^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12102 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 1^0 + 0^1 + 2^{17}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 0^1 + 2^3}$$

$$12123 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 1^0 + 2^{17} + 3^{13}}{1^0 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 2^7 + 3^2}$$

$$12126 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^8 - 1^0 + 2^{12} + 6^5}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12127 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^3 + 1^0 - 2^{15} + 7^6}{1^0 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$12133 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{16} - 1^0 - 3^3 + 3^{13}}{1^0 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 3^3 + 3^4}$$

$$12134 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 - 1^0 + 3^{11} + 4^8}{1^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 4^2}$$

$$12135 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{20} + 1^0 - 3^8 + 5^9}{1^0 + 2^6 + 1^0 + 3^1 + 5^1}$$

$$12138 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{14} + 1^0 + 3^{13} + 8^0}{-1^0 + 2^7 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$12139 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{16} - 1^0 + 3^{13} + 9^3}{1^0 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 3^3 + 9^2}$$

$$12143 := \frac{1^0 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 4^9 - 3^{11}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 3^1}$$

$$12146 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^9 - 1^0 - 4^3 + 6^7}{1^0 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 4^2 + 6^0}$$

$$12147 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{20} + 1^0 + 4^{11} + 7^3}{-1^0 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 4^4 + 7^0}$$

$$12149 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{15} - 1^0 + 4^{10} - 9^2}{1^0 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 4^1 + 9^2}$$

$$12153 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{19} + 1^0 + 5^1 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 2^5 + 1^0 + 5^1 + 3^2}$$

$$12157 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^3 + 1^0 + 5^5 + 7^7}{1^0 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 7^2}$$

$$12159 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^3 + 1^0 + 5^9 + 9^7}{1^0 + 2^3 + 1^0 + 5^4 - 9^2}$$

$$12160 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^8 + 1^0 + 6^7 + 0^1}{-1^0 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 6^1 + 0^0}$$

$$12162 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^6 - 1^0 + 6^8 - 2^{19}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 - 6^2 + 2^7}$$

$$12163 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{10} + 1^0 + 6^6 + 3^{13}}{1^0 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 6^2 + 3^4}$$

$$12165 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^4 + 1^0 + 6^7 - 5^3}{-1^0 - 2^0 - 1^0 + 6^0 + 5^2}$$

$$12167 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{19} - 1^0 + 6^4 - 7^4}{1^0 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 6^2 + 7^0}$$

$$12168 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^3 + 1^0 + 6^7 - 8^2}{-1^0 + 2^4 - 1^0 + 6^0 + 8^1}$$

$$12169 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{18} + 1^0 - 6^2 - 9^4}{1^0 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$12173 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 - 1^0 + 7^3 + 3^{13}}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 7^2 + 3^4}$$

$$12175 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{12} + 1^0 + 7^6 + 5^1}{1^0 + 2^1 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 5^1}$$

$$12183 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{16} - 1^0 + 8^2 + 3^9}{1^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 3^1}$$

$$12187 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^6 - 1^0 + 8^8 - 7^6}{-1^0 + 2^9 + 1^0 + 8^3 + 7^3}$$

$$12197 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{10} + 1^0 + 9^4 + 7^5}{1^0 - 2^1 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$12202 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^8 + 2^{12} - 0^0 + 2^{15}}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 2^0}$$

$$12203 := \frac{1^0 + 2^4 + 2^{18} + 0^1 + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^5 + 0^0 + 3^0}$$

$$12205 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 - 2^6 + 0^0 + 5^8}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 0^0 + 5^2}$$

$$12206 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{10} + 2^{17} + 0^0 - 6^6}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 0^1 + 6^0}$$

$$12209 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{13} + 0^0 - 9^2}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12213 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^5 + 2^{11} + 1^0 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 3^0}$$

$$12214 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{11} - 2^{15} + 1^0 + 4^{10}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^4 + 1^0 + 4^3}$$

$$12215 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^8 + 1^0 + 5^8}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 1^0 + 5^2}$$

$$12216 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{15} + 1^0 - 6^3}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12217 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{11} + 2^{16} - 1^0 - 7^4}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 7^0}$$

$$12218 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{10} + 2^{19} - 1^0 + 8^2}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^5 + 1^0 + 8^1}$$

$$12219 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^1 + 2^{11} + 1^0 + 9^5}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12222 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 - 2^6 + 2^{12} + 2^{13}}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$$

$$12223 := \frac{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^4 + 2^{11} + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0}$$

$$12224 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^0 - 2^6 - 2^{12} + 4^7}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0}$$

$$12225 := \frac{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^{17} + 5^6}{1^1 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 5^1}$$

$$12226 := \frac{1^0 - 2^6 + 2^{12} + 2^{13} + 6^0}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12227 := \frac{1^0 + 2^5 + 2^9 + 2^{20} + 7^4}{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 7^2}$$

$$12229 := \frac{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^{13} + 2^{19} + 9^6}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 9^2}$$

$$12230 := \frac{1^0 - 2^4 - 2^{10} + 3^{14} + 0^1}{-1^0 + 2^7 + 2^8 + 3^2 - 0^0}$$

$$12231 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^9 + 2^{18} + 3^9 - 1^0}{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 1^0}$$

$$12232 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^6 + 2^{12} + 3^2 + 2^{13}}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$12233 := \frac{1^0 + 2^6 + 2^{11} + 3^1 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 3^0}$$

$$12234 := \frac{1^0 + 2^3 + 2^{11} + 3^{10} + 4^3}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 4^0}$$

$$12235 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{15} + 2^{17} + 3^9 + 5^0}{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^0}$$

$$12236 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{15} + 2^{18} + 3^5 + 6^7}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 6^2}$$

$$12237 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^8 - 2^{12} - 3^6 + 7^5}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 7^0}$$

$$12238 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^5 + 2^{13} - 3^4 + 8^4}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 8^0}$$

$$12239 := \frac{1^0 + 2^4 + 2^{11} + 3^4 + 9^5}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12240 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{11} + 2^{19} - 4^2 + 0^0}{1^0 + 2^3 + 2^5 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$12242 := \frac{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^{13} + 4^{10} + 2^{15}}{1^3 + 2^3 + 2^3 + 4^3 + 2^3}$$

$$12243 := \frac{1^0 + 2^7 + 2^{11} + 4^8 + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 3^0}$$

$$12245 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{10} + 2^{18} + 4^{12} + 5^7}{1^0 + 2^2 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 5^4}$$

$$12246 := \frac{1^0 - 2^7 + 2^{15} + 4^6 + 6^0}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12247 := \frac{1^0 + 2^8 + 2^{12} + 4^{13} + 7^3}{1^0 + 2^4 + 2^{10} + 4^6 + 7^3}$$

$$12249 := \frac{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^{13} + 4^7 - 9^2}{-1^0 - 2^0 - 2^0 + 4^1 + 9^0}$$

$$12250 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{15} + 2^{18} + 5^6 + 0^1}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^4 + 5^0 + 0^0}$$

$$12251 := \frac{1^0 - 2^8 + 2^{18} - 5^7 + 1^0}{1^0 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 1^0}$$

$$12252 := \frac{1^0 + 2^4 - 2^{10} - 5^5 + 2^{14}}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$12253 := \frac{1^0 + 2^8 + 2^{20} + 5^9 + 3^3}{1^0 + 2^6 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 3^3}$$

$$12254 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 + 2^{14} + 5^4 + 4^{10}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^4 + 5^1 + 4^3}$$

$$12255 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{15} + 5^2 - 5^3}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 5^0}$$

$$12256 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^9 - 2^{12} + 5^6 + 6^3}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12257 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{10} + 2^{12} + 5^5 + 7^8}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 5^3 + 7^3}$$

$$12258 := \frac{1^0 + 2^7 + 2^{17} + 5^5 + 8^3}{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 8^0}$$

$$12259 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 2^{15} + 5^0 + 9^7}{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^8 + 5^3 + 9^1}$$

$$12260 := \frac{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 6^8 + 0^0}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^7 + 6^1 + 0^0}$$

$$12261 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^8 + 2^{16} + 6^5 - 1^0}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$12262 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^7 - 2^{12} - 6^0 + 2^{16}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 2^0}$$

$$12263 := \frac{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^{11} + 6^3 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0}$$

$$12264 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^{20} - 6^1 + 4^{10}}{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 4^1}$$

$$12265 := \frac{1^0 + 2^5 + 2^{12} + 6^9 + 5^1}{1^0 + 2^5 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 5^4}$$

$$12266 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{14} + 2^{20} + 6^0 - 6^7}{-1^0 + 2^0 - 2^3 + 6^2 + 6^2}$$

$$12267 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^4 - 2^5 + 6^5 + 7^5}{-1^0 - 2^0 - 2^0 + 6^1 - 7^0}$$

$$12268 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^7 - 2^{20} + 6^9 + 8^0}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 2^3 + 6^3 + 8^3}$$

$$12269 := \frac{1^0 + 2^7 + 2^{15} + 6^2 + 9^6}{1^0 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 6^2 + 9^0}$$

$$12270 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{17} + 2^{19} + 7^6 + 0^1}{1^0 + 2^2 + 2^3 + 7^2 + 0^0}$$

$$12271 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{15} - 7^2 - 1^0}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 1^0}$$

$$12272 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^3 + 2^{12} - 7^1 + 2^{13}}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 2^0}$$

$$12273 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{13} - 7^1 - 3^2}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 3^0}$$

$$12274 := \frac{1^0 - 2^3 - 2^{12} - 7^1 + 4^7}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 4^0}$$

$$12275 := \frac{1^0 + 2^5 + 2^{10} + 7^7 + 5^8}{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^6 + 7^1 + 5^2}$$

$$12276 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{15} + 2^{15} + 7^3 + 6^5}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 7^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12277 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{11} + 2^{14} + 7^3 - 7^4}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$12278 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 + 2^{14} + 7^6 + 8^3}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 7^1 + 8^0}$$

$$12279 := \frac{1^0 - 2^4 + 2^{11} + 7^5 - 9^4}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12280 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^3 + 2^{13} + 8^4 + 0^0}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 0^0}$$

$$12281 := \frac{1^0 - 2^4 - 2^{13} + 8^5 + 1^0}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^1 + 8^0 + 1^0}$$

$$12282 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 - 2^2 + 8^4 + 2^{13}}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 2^0}$$

$$12283 := \frac{1^0 + 2^8 + 2^{17} + 8^3 + 3^{12}}{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^4 + 8^1 + 3^3}$$

$$12284 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 - 2^1 - 8^4 + 4^7}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 4^0}$$

$$12285 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^{13} + 8^4 - 5^0}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 5^0}$$

$$12286 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^1 + 2^{13} + 8^4 + 6^0}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12287 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^{13} + 8^4 + 7^0}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$12288 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^0 + 2^{12} + 8^4 + 8^4}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$12289 := \frac{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^{17} + 8^4 + 9^1}{1^0 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12290 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{13} + 9^0 + 0^1}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 0^0}$$

$$12291 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{13} + 9^0 + 1^0}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 1^0}$$

$$12292 := \frac{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^{12} + 9^0 + 2^{13}}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$12293 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{13} + 9^0 + 3^1}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$12294 := \frac{1^0 + 2^6 + 2^{17} + 9^0 + 4^6}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 9^0 + 4^1}$$

$$12295 := \frac{1^0 + 2^5 + 2^{19} + 9^1 + 5^7}{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 9^1 + 5^1}$$

$$12296 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{17} + 9^2 + 6^1}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 9^0 + 6^1}$$

$$12297 := \frac{1^0 + 2^1 + 2^5 + 9^5 + 7^4}{1^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 7^0}$$

$$12298 := \frac{1^0 + 2^3 + 2^{13} + 9^0 + 8^4}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 8^0}$$

$$12299 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{12} + 2^{13} + 9^0 + 9^1}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12302 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 3^3 + 0^1 + 2^{14}}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 2^1}$$

$$12303 := \frac{1^0 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 0^0 + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 0^0 + 3^2}$$

$$12304 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{12} + 3^4 + 0^1 + 4^8}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 0^0 + 4^0}$$

$$12305 := \frac{1^0 - 2^9 + 3^{16} + 0^1 - 5^6}{1^0 + 2^7 + 3^5 + 0^1 + 5^5}$$

$$12306 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{19} + 3^{11} + 0^1 + 6^1}{1^0 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 0^0 + 6^2}$$

$$12307 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{10} + 3^0 + 0^1 + 7^7}{1^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 0^1 + 7^2}$$

$$12308 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{14} + 3^4 + 0^1 + 8^5}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 8^0}$$

$$12309 := \frac{1^0 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 0^1 + 9^6}{1^0 + 2^5 + 3^0 + 0^1 + 9^1}$$

$$12313 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{15} + 3^7 + 1^0 + 3^{12}}{1^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 1^0 + 3^3}$$

$$12315 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{11} - 3^7 + 1^0 + 5^7}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$12320 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^7 + 3^{16} - 2^9 + 0^1}{-1^0 + 2^7 - 3^6 + 2^{12} + 0^1}$$

$$12321 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^8 + 3^{18} + 2^{20} + 1^0}{1^0 - 2^9 - 3^6 + 2^{15} + 1^0}$$

$$12322 := \frac{1^0 + 2^8 + 3^{10} + 2^8 + 2^{11}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 2^0}$$

$$12323 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{10} + 3^{11} + 2^{11} + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 2^4 + 3^2}$$

$$12324 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 3^7 + 2^{17} + 4^4}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 2^2 + 4^1}$$

$$12325 := \frac{1^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 2^{15} + 5^7}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 5^1}$$

$$12326 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{12} + 3^9 + 2^{20} + 6^1}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 2^1 + 6^0}$$

$$12327 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{17} + 3^{11} + 2^{17} + 7^5}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 2^0 + 7^1}$$

$$12328 := \frac{1^0 + 2^2 + 3^{19} + 2^5 + 8^{10}}{1^0 + 2^2 + 3^{11} + 2^7 + 8^4}$$

$$12329 := \frac{1^0 + 2^2 + 3^{11} + 2^{17} + 9^0}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 2^2 + 9^1}$$

$$12330 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{10} + 3^7 + 3^{15} + 0^0}{-1^0 - 2^{10} + 3^0 + 3^7 + 0^0}$$

$$12331 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{11} - 3^8 + 3^{11} + 1^0}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 3^2 + 1^0}$$

$$12332 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^0 + 3^4 + 3^{11} + 2^{17}}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 2^4}$$

$$12333 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 3^3 - 3^8 + 3^{11}}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 3^2}$$

$$12334 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 3^{11} + 4^0}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 3^2 + 4^1}$$

$$12335 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} - 3^4 + 3^9 - 5^5}{1^0 - 2^1 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 5^0}$$

$$12336 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{20} - 3^2 - 3^2 + 6^0}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 3^4 + 6^0}$$

$$12337 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 3^{11} + 7^2}{1^1 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 7^1}$$

$$12338 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{13} + 3^3 + 3^{14} + 8^0}{1^0 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 3^5 + 8^2}$$

$$12339 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 + 3^9 + 3^{11} + 9^2}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$12340 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{11} + 3^{17} - 4^2 + 0^1}{-1^0 - 2^{13} + 3^9 - 4^5 - 0^0}$$

$$12341 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{19} + 3^{13} + 4^7 - 1^0}{1^0 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 1^0}$$

$$12342 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 2^{17}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 2^2}$$

$$12343 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 3^3 + 4^6 + 3^3}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 3^0}$$

$$12344 := \frac{1^0 + 2^6 - 3^2 - 4^6 + 4^7}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 4^0}$$

$$12345 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^7}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^1 + 4^0 + 5^0}$$

$$12346 := \frac{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^{13} + 4^9 + 6^5}{1^0 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 6^0}$$

$$12347 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{19} + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^1}{1^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 7^1}$$

$$12348 := \frac{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^{12} + 4^8 + 8^5}{1^0 + 2^5 + 3^0 + 4^2 + 8^0}$$

$$12349 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{15} + 3^{11} + 4^2 + 9^0}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 4^1 + 9^1}$$

$$12350 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{14} + 3^2 + 5^7 + 0^0}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 0^0}$$

$$12351 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{16} - 3^7 + 5^{12} - 1^0}{-1^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 1^0}$$

$$12352 := \frac{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^4 + 5^7 - 2^{12}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 2^1}$$

$$12353 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{17} + 3^8 + 5^6 + 3^9}{1^1 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 3^1}$$

$$12354 := \frac{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 4^7}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 4^0}$$

$$12355 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{15} + 3^{12} + 5^3 + 5^7}{1^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 5^2}$$

$$12356 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{18} + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^0}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^1}$$

$$12357 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{19} + 3^0 + 5^4 + 7^6}{1^0 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^1}$$

$$12358 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{14} + 3^{12} + 5^7 + 8^0}{1^0 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 8^0}$$

$$12359 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{14} - 3^6 + 5^6 - 9^4}{1^0 - 2^1 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12360 := \frac{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^{12} + 6^2 + 0^0}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 6^2 + 0^0}$$

$$12361 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^5 + 3^{10} - 6^6 + 1^0}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 1^0}$$

$$12362 := \frac{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^{10} + 6^3 + 2^{18}}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 6^1 + 2^4}$$

$$12363 := \frac{1^0 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 6^5 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 3^1}$$

$$12364 := \frac{1^0 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 6^4 + 4^8}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^1 + 6^0 + 4^0}$$

$$12365 := \frac{1^0 + 2^5 + 3^{12} + 6^3 + 5^1}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 6^2 + 5^0}$$

$$12366 := \frac{1^0 + 2^3 + 3^{10} - 6^2 - 6^6}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12367 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{16} + 3^{11} + 6^3 + 7^5}{1^0 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 7^1}$$

$$12368 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 3^{10} + 6^1 + 8^7}{1^0 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 6^2 + 8^0}$$

$$12369 := \frac{1^0 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 6^7 + 9^5}{1^0 + 2^2 + 3^2 + 6^1 + 9^1}$$

$$12370 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{10} + 3^{13} + 7^8 + 0^0}{1^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 7^3 + 0^1}$$

$$12371 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 7^9 + 1^0}{1^0 + 2^{10} + 3^7 + 7^2 + 1^0}$$

$$12372 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^0 + 3^{10} + 7^7 + 2^{13}}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 2^6}$$

$$12373 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{19} + 3^6 + 7^6 + 3^6}{1^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 7^1 + 3^3}$$

$$12374 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 3^7 + 7^9 + 4^0}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 4^5}$$

$$12375 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 3^3 + 7^2 + 5^9}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 7^2 + 5^2}$$

$$12376 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{17} - 3^9 - 7^1 + 6^0}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 7^1 + 6^0}$$

$$12377 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{13} - 3^5 - 7^0 + 7^5}{1^0 - 2^1 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 7^0}$$

$$12378 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{13} - 3^5 + 7^5 + 8^0}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 - 7^1 + 8^1}$$

$$12379 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} - 3^5 + 7^5 + 9^0}{1^0 - 2^1 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12382 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{10} + 3^2 + 8^4 + 2^{17}}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 8^0 + 2^2}$$

$$12383 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 8^3 + 3^{12}}{1^0 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 8^1 + 3^3}$$

$$12384 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^4 + 3^4 - 8^4 + 4^7}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 4^0}$$

$$12385 := \frac{1^0 + 2^2 + 3^{11} + 8^5 + 5^4}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 8^0 + 5^1}$$

$$12386 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 8^4 + 6^5}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12387 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{13} - 3^5 + 8^4 + 7^3}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$12388 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{20} + 3^5 + 8^2 + 8^4}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^4 + 8^0 + 8^0}$$

$$12389 := \frac{1^0 + 2^5 - 3^9 + 8^5 - 9^3}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12390 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{14} + 3^{13} - 9^1 + 0^0}{-1^0 - 2^5 + 3^4 + 9^2 + 0^0}$$

$$12391 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^{13} + 3^{13} - 9^2 - 1^0}{-1^0 - 2^5 + 3^4 + 9^2 - 1^0}$$

$$12392 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 + 3^{11} - 9^2 - 2^{16}}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 2^2}$$

$$12393 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^0 - 3^6 + 9^4 + 3^8}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 3^0}$$

$$12394 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^0 - 3^{11} + 9^6 + 4^{11}}{1^0 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 9^2 + 4^4}$$

$$12395 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 3^5 + 9^3 + 5^6}{1^0 - 2^1 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 5^0}$$

$$12396 := \frac{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 9^5 - 6^6}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12397 := \frac{1^0 + 2^8 + 3^{15} + 9^4 + 7^0}{1^0 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 9^3 + 7^3}$$

$$12398 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{19} - 3^{11} + 9^0 + 8^0}{1^0 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 9^1 + 8^1}$$

$$12399 := \frac{1^0 - 2^{18} + 3^{11} - 9^2 + 9^6}{1^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 9^1 + 9^1}$$

$$12403 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{14} + 4^9 + 0^0 + 3^{13}}{1^0 + 2^2 + 4^3 + 0^0 + 3^4}$$

$$12406 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{17} + 4^6 + 0^0 + 6^4}{1^0 + 2^1 + 4^0 + 0^0 + 6^1}$$

$$12407 := \frac{1^0 + 2^5 + 4^{10} + 0^1 + 7^6}{-1^0 + 2^3 - 4^4 + 0^1 + 7^3}$$

$$12409 := \frac{1^0 - 2^6 + 4^{11} + 0^1 + 9^0}{-1^0 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 0^0 + 9^2}$$

$$12413 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^5 + 4^{10} + 1^0 + 3^8}{1^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 3^4}$$

$$12414 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 1^0 + 4^7}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 4^0}$$

$$12415 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 4^6 + 1^0 + 5^3}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 5^0}$$

$$12416 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{19} + 4^7 + 1^0 - 6^7}{1^0 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 1^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12418 := \frac{1^0 + 2^7 + 4^7 + 1^0 - 8^4}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 8^0}$$

$$12419 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{17} - 4^5 + 1^0 + 9^4}{1^0 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 1^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12422 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 - 4^4 - 2^{10} + 2^{18}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 2^4}$$

$$12423 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{15} + 4^{10} + 2^{19} + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 2^7 + 3^1}$$

$$12424 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^3 + 4^0 - 2^{17} + 4^{13}}{-1^0 + 2^4 + 4^4 + 2^{10} + 4^6}$$

$$12425 := \frac{1^0 + 2^3 + 4^5 + 2^{13} + 5^6}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 5^0}$$

$$12426 := \frac{1^0 + 2^1 + 4^{13} + 2^{14} + 6^0}{1^0 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 2^3 + 6^4}$$

$$12427 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 2^{13} + 7^3}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^0 + 2^1 + 7^0}$$

$$12429 := \frac{1^0 + 2^3 + 4^{11} + 2^7 + 9^4}{1^0 + 2^3 + 4^3 + 2^8 + 9^1}$$

$$12430 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{20} + 4^{11} - 3^{14} + 0^1}{1^0 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 3^3 + 0^0}$$

$$12431 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{19} + 4^0 - 3^7 + 1^0}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^2 + 3^3 + 1^0}$$

$$12432 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 4^1 + 3^7 + 2^{13}}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 2^0}$$

$$12433 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 4^{10} + 3^2 + 3^3}{1^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 3^4}$$

$$12434 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 4^5 + 3^7 + 4^9}{1^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 3^1 + 4^2}$$

$$12435 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{13} + 4^{10} + 3^4 + 5^3}{1^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 3^4 + 5^0}$$

$$12436 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 3^9 - 6^5}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12437 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{17} + 4^1 + 3^{11} + 7^7}{1^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 3^4 + 7^1}$$

$$12438 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^7 + 4^7 + 3^6 + 8^5}{-1^0 - 2^0 - 4^0 - 3^0 + 8^1}$$

$$12439 := \frac{1^0 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 3^{11} + 9^5}{1^1 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$12443 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{17} - 4^2 - 4^3 - 3^8}{1^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 4^1 + 3^1}$$

$$12445 := \frac{1^0 + 2^1 - 4^7 + 4^8 + 5^4}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^0 + 4^1 + 5^0}$$

$$12446 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 4^{10} + 6^6}{1^0 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 4^3 + 6^1}$$

$$12447 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^3 - 4^5 - 4^5 + 7^7}{1^0 + 2^3 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 7^2}$$

$$12449 := \frac{1^0 - 2^5 - 4^3 + 4^8 + 9^5}{-1^0 - 2^0 - 4^0 + 4^1 + 9^1}$$

$$12450 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{19} + 4^8 - 5^8 + 0^1}{1^0 + 2^3 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 0^0}$$

$$12451 := \frac{1^0 + 2^9 - 4^7 + 5^7 + 1^0}{1^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$12452 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^3 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 2^7}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 2^0}$$

$$12453 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{19} + 4^1 + 5^9 + 3^6}{1^0 + 2^3 + 4^3 + 5^3 + 3^0}$$

$$12454 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{19} + 4^7 + 5^{12} + 4^{10}}{1^0 + 2^3 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 4^6}$$

$$12455 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{11} + 4^4 + 5^1 + 5^9}{1^0 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 5^3}$$

$$12456 := \frac{1^0 - 2^7 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 6^1}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12457 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{14} + 4^{11} + 5^9 + 7^4}{1^0 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^2}$$

$$12458 := \frac{1^0 + 2^3 + 4^7 + 5^8 + 8^4}{1^0 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 8^0}$$

$$12459 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^7 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 9^0}{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 + 9^0}$$

$$12460 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^5 + 4^{11} - 6^5 + 0^0}{-1^0 + 2^6 - 4^5 + 6^4 + 0^0}$$

$$12462 := \frac{-1^0 - 2^0 + 4^8 + 6^6 - 2^5}{1^0 + 2^0 + 4^1 + 6^0 + 2^1}$$

$$12463 := \frac{1^0 + 2^3 + 4^8 + 6^2 + 3^{10}}{1^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 3^0}$$

$$12464 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^{15} + 4^0 - 6^5 - 4^3}{-1^0 - 2^0 - 4^0 + 6^0 + 4^1}$$

$$12465 := \frac{1^0 + 2^5 + 4^0 + 6^8 + 5^5}{1^0 + 2^1 + 4^0 + 6^1 + 5^3}$$

$$12466 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^1 + 4^8 + 6^0 + 6^6}{1^0 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 6^0 + 6^0}$$

$$12467 := \frac{1^0 + 2^{20} + 4^{12} + 6^4 + 7^7}{1^0 + 2^7 + 4^3 + 6^4 + 7^1}$$

$$12468 := \frac{-1^0 + 2^5 + 4^{10} - 6^4 + 8^0}{1^0 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 6^0 + 8^2}$$

$$13787 := \frac{-1^6 + 3^6 - 7^6 + 8^6 - 7^6}{-1^1 - 3^1 + 7^1 - 8^1 + 7^1}$$

$$14562 := \frac{-1^6 - 4^6 + 5^6 + 6^6 + 2^6}{1^1 + 4^1 - 5^1 + 6^1 - 2^1}$$

$$14705 := \frac{-1^5 + 4^5 + 7^5 - 0^5 - 5^5}{1^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 - 0^0 - 5^0}$$

$$15501 := \frac{1^9 + 5^9 + 5^9 - 0^9 + 1^9}{1^3 + 5^3 + 5^3 - 0^3 + 1^3}$$

$$16527 := \frac{-1^6 + 6^6 - 5^6 + 2^6 + 7^6}{-1^1 + 6^1 - 5^1 + 2^1 + 7^1}$$

$$21351 := \frac{2^8 - 1^8 - 3^8 + 5^8 - 1^8}{2^2 - 1^2 - 3^2 + 5^2 - 1^2}$$

$$21438 := \frac{-2^6 + 1^6 - 4^6 - 3^6 + 8^6}{2^1 + 1^1 + 4^1 - 3^1 + 8^1}$$

$$23360 := \frac{2^6 + 3^6 - 3^6 + 6^6 - 0^6}{2^1 + 3^1 + 3^1 - 6^1 - 0^1}$$

$$24203 := \frac{2^8 + 4^8 + 2^8 - 0^8 + 3^8}{2^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 - 3^0}$$

$$25497 := \frac{-2^6 + 5^6 + 4^6 + 9^6 - 7^6}{2^1 - 5^1 + 4^1 + 9^1 + 7^1}$$

$$25869 := \frac{-2^6 - 5^6 - 8^6 - 6^6 + 9^6}{-2^1 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 6^1 - 9^1}$$

$$26048 := \frac{2^5 - 6^5 - 0^5 + 4^5 + 8^5}{2^0 + 6^0 + 0^0 - 4^0 - 8^0}$$

$$26889 := \frac{2^6 + 6^6 + 8^6 + 8^6 + 9^6}{-2^2 - 6^2 + 8^2 - 8^2 + 9^2}$$

$$27128 := \frac{2^6 + 7^6 - 1^6 - 2^6 + 8^6}{2^1 + 7^1 - 1^1 - 2^1 + 8^1}$$

$$32832 := \frac{3^5 + 2^5 + 8^5 - 3^5 + 2^5}{3^0 + 2^0 + 8^0 - 3^0 - 2^0}$$

$$33169 := \frac{-3^5 - 3^5 - 1^5 + 6^5 + 9^5}{3^1 + 3^1 - 1^1 + 6^1 - 9^1}$$

$$33219 := \frac{3^6 - 3^6 + 2^6 - 1^6 + 9^6}{3^1 + 3^1 + 2^1 - 1^1 + 9^1}$$

$$33824 := \frac{3^5 - 3^5 + 8^5 + 2^5 + 4^5}{3^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 - 2^0 - 4^0}$$

$$35523 := \frac{3^8 + 5^8 + 5^8 + 2^8 - 3^8}{3^2 + 5^2 - 5^2 + 2^2 + 3^2}$$

$$39339 := \frac{3^6 + 9^6 - 3^6 - 3^6 + 9^6}{3^1 + 9^1 + 3^1 + 3^1 + 9^1}$$

$$39393 := \frac{3^6 + 9^6 + 3^6 + 9^6 - 3^6}{3^1 + 9^1 + 3^1 + 9^1 + 3^1}$$

$$43213 := \frac{4^{13} - 3^{13} - 2^{13} + 1^{13} - 3^{13}}{4^5 + 3^5 - 2^5 + 1^5 + 3^5}$$

$$45616 := \frac{4^8 + 5^8 + 6^8 - 1^8 - 6^8}{4^1 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 1^1 - 6^1}$$

$$46624 := \frac{4^6 + 6^6 + 6^6 - 2^6 - 4^6}{-4^1 + 6^1 + 6^1 - 2^1 - 4^1}$$

$$46871 := \frac{-4^6 - 6^6 + 8^6 - 7^6 - 1^6}{-4^1 + 6^1 + 8^1 - 7^1 - 1^1}$$

$$48495 := \frac{4^5 + 8^5 + 4^5 + 9^5 + 5^5}{4^1 + 8^1 + 4^1 - 9^1 - 5^1}$$

$$49625 := \frac{-4^6 + 9^6 - 6^6 - 2^6 + 5^6}{4^1 + 9^1 - 6^1 - 2^1 + 5^1}$$

$$52144 := \frac{5^8 - 2^8 - 1^8 + 4^8 + 4^8}{5^1 - 2^1 - 1^1 + 4^1 + 4^1}$$

$$54748 := \frac{5^5 + 4^5 + 7^5 + 4^5 + 8^5}{5^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 - 4^0 - 8^0}$$

$$54900 := \frac{-5^5 - 4^5 + 9^5 - 0^5 - 0^5}{5^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 - 0^0 - 0^0}$$

$$54901 := \frac{-5^5 - 4^5 + 9^5 - 0^5 + 1^5}{5^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 - 0^0 - 1^0}$$

$$56393 := \frac{-5^6 + 6^6 + 3^6 + 9^6 + 3^6}{-5^1 + 6^1 + 3^1 + 9^1 - 3^1}$$

$$60885 := \frac{-6^5 - 0^5 + 8^5 + 8^5 + 5^5}{6^0 + 0^0 + 8^0 - 8^0 - 5^0}$$

$$62152 := \frac{6^6 - 2^6 - 1^6 + 5^6 - 2^6}{6^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 - 5^0 - 2^0}$$

$$62396 := \frac{6^6 - 2^6 - 3^6 + 9^6 + 6^6}{6^1 - 2^1 + 3^1 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$63639 := \frac{6^8 - 3^8 + 6^8 - 3^8 + 9^8}{6^3 + 3^3 - 6^3 - 3^3 + 9^3}$$

$$64157 := \frac{-6^7 - 4^7 + 1^7 - 5^7 + 7^7}{6^1 + 4^1 - 1^1 + 5^1 - 7^1}$$

$$68354 := \frac{-6^7 + 8^7 + 3^7 + 5^7 + 4^7}{-6^2 + 8^2 - 3^2 + 5^2 - 4^2}$$

$$69347 := \frac{-6^5 + 9^5 + 3^5 + 4^5 + 7^5}{6^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 - 4^0 - 7^0}$$

$$74360 := \frac{7^6 + 4^6 - 3^6 - 6^6 - 0^6}{7^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 - 6^0 - 0^0}$$

$$74361 := \frac{7^6 + 4^6 - 3^6 - 6^6 + 1^6}{7^0 + 4^0 + 3^0 - 6^0 - 1^0}$$

$$76285 := \frac{-7^7 - 6^7 - 2^7 + 8^7 - 5^7}{7^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 - 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$82151 := \frac{8^6 - 2^6 - 1^6 - 5^6 - 1^6}{8^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 - 1^0}$$

$$92727 := \frac{9^5 + 2^5 + 7^5 + 2^5 + 7^5}{9^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 - 2^0 - 7^0}$$

$$93084 := \frac{9^5 + 3^5 - 0^5 + 8^5 + 4^5}{9^0 + 3^0 + 0^0 - 8^0 - 4^0}$$

$$94509 := \frac{9^7 + 4^7 + 5^7 - 0^7 - 9^7}{9^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 - 0^0 - 9^0}$$

$$94651 := \frac{9^6 + 4^6 - 6^6 - 5^6 - 1^6}{9^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 5^0 + 1^0}$$

$$95139 := \frac{9^6 - 5^6 + 1^6 - 3^6 + 9^6}{9^1 - 5^1 + 1^1 - 3^1 + 9^1}$$

3.6 Six Digits and More

$$118378 := \frac{1^{12} - 1^{12} + 8^{12} - 3^{12} + 7^{12} - 8^{12}}{1^6 - 1^6 + 8^6 - 3^6 + 7^6 - 8^6}$$

$$122347 := \frac{1^6 - 2^6 - 2^6 + 3^6 + 4^6 + 7^6}{1^1 + 2^1 - 2^1 + 3^1 + 4^1 - 7^1}$$

$$122473 := \frac{-1^6 + 2^6 - 2^6 + 4^6 + 7^6 + 3^6}{1^1 + 2^1 - 2^1 - 4^1 + 7^1 - 3^1}$$

$$131832 := \frac{-1^6 + 3^6 - 1^6 + 8^6 + 3^6 + 2^6}{1^0 + 3^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 - 3^0 - 2^0}$$

$$133209 := \frac{1^6 + 3^6 + 3^6 - 2^6 - 0^6 + 9^6}{1^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 0^0 - 9^0}$$

$$134804 := \frac{1^6 - 3^6 + 4^6 + 8^6 - 0^6 + 4^6}{1^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 8^0 - 0^0 - 4^0}$$

$$142740 := \frac{1^7 + 4^7 + 2^7 + 7^7 + 4^7 - 0^7}{1^0 + 4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 0^0}$$

$$145934 := \frac{-1^7 - 4^7 - 5^7 + 9^7 - 3^7 - 4^7}{-1^2 - 4^2 - 5^2 + 9^2 + 3^2 - 4^2}$$

$$159669 := \frac{-1^9 - 5^9 + 9^9 + 6^9 + 6^9 - 9^9}{-1^2 + 5^2 + 9^2 - 6^2 - 6^2 + 9^2}$$

$$161595 := \frac{1^6 - 6^6 - 1^6 + 5^6 + 9^6 - 5^6}{-1^1 + 6^1 - 1^1 - 5^1 + 9^1 - 5^1}$$

$$163575 := \frac{-1^6 + 6^6 - 3^6 + 5^6 + 7^6 - 5^6}{-1^1 + 6^1 + 3^1 + 5^1 - 7^1 - 5^1}$$

$$169239 := \frac{1^6 - 6^6 + 9^6 - 2^6 - 3^6 + 9^6}{1^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 9^0}$$

$$173529 := \frac{-1^8 + 7^8 - 3^8 - 5^8 + 2^8 + 9^8}{-1^3 - 7^3 + 3^3 - 5^3 - 2^3 + 9^3}$$

$$174961 := \frac{1^6 + 7^6 + 4^6 + 9^6 + 6^6 + 1^6}{1^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 - 1^0}$$

$$187848 := \frac{-1^6 + 8^6 + 7^6 + 8^6 - 4^6 - 8^6}{1^0 + 8^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 - 4^0 - 8^0}$$

$$188673 := \frac{-1^{10} + 8^{10} - 8^{10} - 6^{10} + 7^{10} + 3^{10}}{-1^3 + 8^3 + 8^3 - 6^3 + 7^3 + 3^3}$$

$$194979 := \frac{1^5 + 9^5 + 4^5 + 9^5 + 7^5 + 9^5}{-1^1 + 9^1 + 4^1 - 9^1 + 7^1 - 9^1}$$

$$195773 := \frac{-1^6 + 9^6 + 5^6 + 7^6 + 7^6 + 3^6}{1^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 7^0 - 3^0}$$

$$231591 := \frac{2^7 + 3^7 + 1^7 + 5^7 + 9^7 + 1^7}{2^1 + 3^1 + 1^1 + 5^1 + 9^1 + 1^1}$$

$$234513 := \frac{-2^8 + 3^8 + 4^8 + 5^8 - 1^8 + 3^8}{2^0 + 3^0 + 4^0 + 5^0 - 1^0 - 3^0}$$

$$243412 := \frac{-2^{12} + 4^{12} + 3^{12} + 4^{12} - 1^{12} - 2^{12}}{-2^3 + 4^3 + 3^3 + 4^3 + 1^3 - 2^3}$$

$$244800 := \frac{2^8 - 4^8 - 4^8 + 8^8 - 0^8 - 0^8}{2^2 + 4^2 - 4^2 + 8^2 - 0^2 - 0^2}$$

$$246211 := \frac{2^9 + 4^9 + 6^9 + 2^9 - 1^9 - 1^9}{-2^2 + 4^2 + 6^2 - 2^2 - 1^2 - 1^2}$$

$$250269 := \frac{2^6 + 5^6 - 0^6 + 2^6 - 6^6 + 9^6}{2^0 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 - 6^0 - 9^0}$$

$$257972 := \frac{2^6 - 5^6 + 7^6 + 9^6 - 7^6 + 2^6}{2^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 - 7^0 - 2^0}$$

$$263870 := \frac{2^7 - 6^7 - 3^7 + 8^7 + 7^7 - 0^7}{2^1 + 6^1 + 3^1 - 8^1 + 7^1 - 0^1}$$

$$271868 := \frac{2^7 + 7^7 + 1^7 + 8^7 - 6^7 - 8^7}{2^0 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 - 6^0 - 8^0}$$

$$284983 := \frac{-2^7 - 8^7 - 4^7 + 9^7 - 8^7 - 3^7}{2^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 - 8^0 - 3^0}$$

$$291064 := \frac{-2^6 + 9^6 - 1^6 - 0^6 + 6^6 + 4^6}{2^0 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 0^0 - 6^0 - 4^0}$$

$$306979 := \frac{3^6 - 0^6 + 6^6 + 9^6 + 7^6 + 9^6}{3^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 7^0 - 9^0}$$

$$315575 := \frac{-3^9 + 1^9 + 5^9 + 5^9 + 7^9 - 5^9}{3^2 + 1^2 + 5^2 + 5^2 + 7^2 + 5^2}$$

$$338729 := \frac{3^6 + 3^6 + 8^6 - 7^6 + 2^6 + 9^6}{3^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 7^0 - 2^0 - 9^0}$$

$$344627 := \frac{3^8 + 4^8 + 4^8 + 6^8 - 2^8 + 7^8}{3^1 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 6^1 - 2^1 + 7^1}$$

$$367903 := \frac{3^7 + 6^7 + 7^7 + 9^7 - 0^7 - 3^7}{-3^1 + 6^1 + 7^1 + 9^1 - 0^1 - 3^1}$$

$$373681 := \frac{3^8 - 7^8 + 3^8 + 6^8 + 8^8 + 1^8}{-3^2 - 7^2 - 3^2 + 6^2 + 8^2 + 1^2}$$

$$377503 := \frac{-3^8 + 7^8 - 7^8 + 5^8 - 0^8 - 3^8}{3^1 + 7^1 - 7^1 - 5^1 - 0^1 + 3^1}$$

$$392267 := \frac{-3^7 + 9^7 - 2^7 - 2^7 + 6^7 + 7^7}{3^1 + 9^1 + 2^1 + 2^1 + 6^1 - 7^1}$$

$$393425 := \frac{3^7 + 9^7 - 3^7 + 4^7 - 2^7 - 5^7}{3^1 + 9^1 + 3^1 + 4^1 - 2^1 - 5^1}$$

$$402589 := \frac{-4^6 - 0^6 + 2^6 + 5^6 + 8^6 + 9^6}{4^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 - 8^0 - 9^0}$$

$$405631 := \frac{-4^8 - 0^8 - 5^8 + 6^8 - 3^8 - 1^8}{-4^1 - 0^1 + 5^1 + 6^1 - 3^1 - 1^1}$$

$$417889 := \frac{4^6 + 1^6 - 7^6 + 8^6 - 8^6 + 9^6}{4^1 - 1^1 + 7^1 + 8^1 - 8^1 - 9^1}$$

$$427175 := \frac{-4^7 - 2^7 + 7^7 + 1^7 + 7^7 + 5^7}{4^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 - 5^0}$$

$$439136 := \frac{4^8 + 3^8 + 9^8 - 1^8 - 3^8 + 6^8}{-4^2 + 3^2 + 9^2 + 1^2 - 3^2 + 6^2}$$

$$456161 := \frac{4^8 + 5^8 + 6^8 + 1^8 - 6^8 - 1^8}{-4^1 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 1^1 - 6^1 - 1^1}$$

$$459792 := \frac{4^8 - 5^8 + 9^8 - 7^8 + 9^8 + 2^8}{-4^2 - 5^2 + 9^2 + 7^2 + 9^2 + 2^2}$$

$$465129 := \frac{-4^6 - 6^6 - 5^6 + 1^6 + 2^6 + 9^6}{-4^1 + 6^1 + 5^1 + 1^1 + 2^1 - 9^1}$$

$$465363 := \frac{-4^7 + 6^7 - 5^7 + 3^7 + 6^7 - 3^7}{-4^1 + 6^1 + 5^1 + 3^1 - 6^1 - 3^1}$$

$$480689 := \frac{-4^6 + 8^6 - 0^6 - 6^6 - 8^6 + 9^6}{4^1 + 8^1 - 0^1 + 6^1 - 8^1 - 9^1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 491428 &:= \frac{4^7 + 9^7 - 1^7 - 4^7 - 2^7 + 8^7}{4^1 + 9^1 - 1^1 - 4^1 - 2^1 + 8^1} \\
 496251 &:= \frac{-4^6 + 9^6 - 6^6 - 2^6 + 5^6 + 1^6}{-4^1 + 9^1 - 6^1 - 2^1 + 5^1 - 1^1} \\
 499536 &:= \frac{-4^8 + 9^8 - 9^8 + 5^8 - 3^8 + 6^8}{4^0 + 9^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 3^0 - 6^0} \\
 521441 &:= \frac{5^8 - 2^8 + 1^8 + 4^8 + 4^8 - 1^8}{5^1 - 2^1 - 1^1 + 4^1 - 4^1 - 1^1} \\
 523929 &:= \frac{-5^6 - 2^6 + 3^6 + 9^6 - 2^6 + 9^6}{5^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 - 2^0 - 9^0} \\
 524544 &:= \frac{5^{11} + 2^{11} + 4^{11} - 5^{11} + 4^{11} - 4^{11}}{5^1 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 5^1 - 4^1 - 4^1} \\
 540238 &:= \frac{5^7 - 4^7 - 0^7 - 2^7 + 3^7 + 8^7}{5^0 + 4^0 + 0^0 + 2^0 + 3^0 - 8^0} \\
 542421 &:= \frac{5^{10} + 4^{10} - 2^{10} - 4^{10} - 2^{10} + 1^{10}}{5^1 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 2^1 + 1^1} \\
 547621 &:= \frac{-5^8 + 4^8 + 7^8 + 6^8 - 2^8 + 1^8}{-5^1 + 4^1 + 7^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 - 1^1} \\
 549369 &:= \frac{-5^6 + 4^6 + 9^6 + 3^6 + 6^6 + 9^6}{5^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 - 6^0 - 9^0} \\
 551585 &:= \frac{5^8 - 5^8 - 1^8 - 5^8 + 8^8 - 5^8}{5^1 + 5^1 + 1^1 + 5^1 + 8^1 + 5^1} \\
 563931 &:= \frac{-5^6 + 6^6 + 3^6 + 9^6 + 3^6 + 1^6}{5^1 + 6^1 + 3^1 - 9^1 - 3^1 - 1^1} \\
 615152 &:= \frac{6^8 - 1^8 + 5^8 - 1^8 + 5^8 - 2^8}{6^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 - 2^0} \\
 623317 &:= \frac{6^{10} + 2^{10} - 3^{10} - 3^{10} - 1^{10} + 7^{10}}{6^3 - 2^3 + 3^3 - 3^3 - 1^3 + 7^3} \\
 623961 &:= \frac{6^6 - 2^6 - 3^6 + 9^6 + 6^6 + 1^6}{-6^1 + 2^1 + 3^1 + 9^1 - 6^1 - 1^1} \\
 629920 &:= \frac{6^9 + 2^9 + 9^9 - 9^9 + 2^9 - 0^9}{-6^1 + 2^1 + 9^1 + 9^1 + 2^1 - 0^1} \\
 630744 &:= \frac{6^8 - 3^8 - 0^8 + 7^8 + 4^8 + 4^8}{-6^1 + 3^1 - 0^1 + 7^1 + 4^1 + 4^1} \\
 744324 &:= \frac{7^8 + 4^8 + 4^8 - 3^8 - 2^8 + 4^8}{7^1 + 4^1 - 4^1 + 3^1 + 2^1 - 4^1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 760921 &:= \frac{7^7 - 6^7 - 0^7 + 9^7 - 2^7 - 1^7}{7^1 - 6^1 - 0^1 + 9^1 - 2^1 - 1^1} \\
 782201 &:= \frac{-7^9 + 8^9 + 2^9 - 2^9 - 0^9 - 1^9}{7^2 + 8^2 + 2^2 + 2^2 - 0^2 - 1^2} \\
 786601 &:= \frac{-7^8 + 8^8 + 6^8 - 6^8 - 0^8 - 1^8}{7^1 + 8^1 + 6^1 - 6^1 - 0^1 - 1^1} \\
 791168 &:= \frac{-7^7 + 9^7 - 1^7 - 1^7 - 6^7 - 8^7}{7^0 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 1^0 - 6^0 - 8^0} \\
 801961 &:= \frac{-8^7 - 0^7 + 1^7 + 9^7 - 6^7 + 1^7}{8^1 - 0^1 - 1^1 - 9^1 + 6^1 - 1^1} \\
 894073 &:= \frac{-8^8 + 9^8 + 4^8 - 0^8 - 7^8 - 3^8}{8^1 + 9^1 - 4^1 - 0^1 + 7^1 + 3^1} \\
 933164 &:= \frac{9^8 + 3^8 - 3^8 - 1^8 + 6^8 + 4^8}{9^2 + 3^2 + 3^2 + 1^2 - 6^2 - 4^2} \\
 997491 &:= \frac{9^8 + 9^8 + 7^8 + 4^8 - 9^8 + 1^8}{9^2 + 9^2 - 7^2 + 4^2 - 9^2 + 1^2} \\
 1035696 &:= \frac{-1^7 - 0^7 - 3^7 - 5^7 - 6^7 + 9^7 - 6^7}{-1^1 - 0^1 + 3^1 + 5^1 - 6^1 + 9^1 - 6^1} \\
 1106259 &:= \frac{1^7 - 1^7 - 0^7 - 6^7 + 2^7 - 5^7 + 9^7}{1^1 - 1^1 - 0^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 - 9^1} \\
 1114749 &:= \frac{1^7 + 1^7 - 1^7 - 4^7 + 7^7 - 4^7 + 9^7}{1^0 + 1^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 - 9^0} \\
 1118481 &:= \frac{-1^{13} - 1^{13} - 1^{13} + 8^{13} + 4^{13} - 8^{13} - 1^{13}}{-1^3 - 1^3 - 1^3 + 8^3 + 4^3 - 8^3 - 1^3} \\
 1121694 &:= \frac{1^7 - 1^7 + 2^7 - 1^7 - 6^7 + 9^7 - 4^7}{1^1 + 1^1 + 2^1 + 1^1 - 6^1 + 9^1 - 4^1} \\
 1147977 &:= \frac{-1^7 - 1^7 - 4^7 - 7^7 + 9^7 - 7^7 - 7^7}{1^1 - 1^1 + 4^1 + 7^1 - 9^1 + 7^1 - 7^1} \\
 1164752 &:= \frac{1^8 - 1^8 + 6^8 - 4^8 + 7^8 - 5^8 + 2^8}{1^1 - 1^1 + 6^1 + 4^1 - 7^1 + 5^1 - 2^1} \\
 1165507 &:= \frac{1^{10} + 1^{10} + 6^{10} + 5^{10} + 5^{10} - 0^{10} + 7^{10}}{1^3 + 1^3 + 6^3 - 5^3 - 5^3 - 0^3 + 7^3} \\
 1169786 &:= \frac{-1^7 - 1^7 + 6^7 + 9^7 + 7^7 - 8^7 - 6^7}{1^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 9^0 + 7^0 - 8^0 - 6^0} \\
 1173925 &:= \frac{-1^9 - 1^9 - 7^9 + 3^9 + 9^9 + 2^9 - 5^9}{-1^3 - 1^3 - 7^3 + 3^3 + 9^3 + 2^3 - 5^3} \\
 1191646 &:= \frac{1^7 - 1^7 + 9^7 - 1^7 + 6^7 - 4^7 - 6^7}{1^1 - 1^1 + 9^1 - 1^1 + 6^1 - 4^1 - 6^1}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$1196438 := \frac{1^7 - 1^7 + 9^7 + 6^7 + 4^7 + 3^7 + 8^7}{-1^1 - 1^1 + 9^1 + 6^1 + 4^1 - 3^1 - 8^1}$$

$$1215209 := \frac{-1^7 - 2^7 - 1^7 + 5^7 - 2^7 - 0^7 + 9^7}{1^1 + 2^1 - 1^1 - 5^1 - 2^1 - 0^1 + 9^1}$$

$$1220959 := \frac{-1^{10} + 2^{10} + 2^{10} - 0^{10} + 9^{10} + 5^{10} - 9^{10}}{-1^1 + 2^1 + 2^1 - 0^1 + 9^1 + 5^1 - 9^1}$$

$$1263641 := \frac{1^{16} + 2^{16} + 6^{16} + 3^{16} - 6^{16} + 4^{16} - 1^{16}}{1^6 + 2^6 + 6^6 - 3^6 - 6^6 + 4^6 + 1^6}$$

$$1368866 := \frac{-1^9 - 3^9 - 6^9 + 8^9 + 8^9 - 6^9 - 6^9}{1^2 + 3^2 + 6^2 + 8^2 + 8^2 + 6^2 - 6^2}$$

$$1395027 := \frac{1^8 - 3^8 + 9^8 + 5^8 - 0^8 - 2^8 - 7^8}{1^1 + 3^1 + 9^1 + 5^1 - 0^1 + 2^1 + 7^1}$$

$$1457520 := \frac{-1^8 + 4^8 + 5^8 + 7^8 - 5^8 - 2^8 - 0^8}{-1^1 + 4^1 + 5^1 - 7^1 + 5^1 - 2^1 - 0^1}$$

$$1488723 := \frac{-1^{10} - 4^{10} + 8^{10} - 8^{10} + 7^{10} + 2^{10} - 3^{10}}{1^2 + 4^2 + 8^2 + 8^2 + 7^2 + 2^2 - 3^2}$$

$$1493363 := \frac{1^7 - 4^7 + 9^7 - 3^7 - 3^7 - 6^7 - 3^7}{1^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 + 3^0 - 6^0 - 3^0}$$

$$1534160 := \frac{-1^9 + 5^9 - 3^9 + 4^9 - 1^9 + 6^9 - 0^9}{1^1 + 5^1 + 3^1 + 4^1 + 1^1 - 6^1 - 0^1}$$

$$1538496 := \frac{-1^8 + 5^8 - 3^8 + 8^8 - 4^8 + 9^8 - 6^8}{1^2 + 5^2 + 3^2 + 8^2 - 4^2 - 9^2 + 6^2}$$

$$1561298 := \frac{-1^8 + 5^8 - 6^8 - 1^8 + 2^8 + 9^8 - 8^8}{1^1 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 1^1 + 2^1 + 9^1 - 8^1}$$

$$1565474 := \frac{1^{10} - 5^{10} - 6^{10} - 5^{10} - 4^{10} + 7^{10} - 4^{10}}{1^3 + 5^3 - 6^3 - 5^3 + 4^3 + 7^3 - 4^3}$$

$$1566773 := \frac{-1^7 - 5^7 + 6^7 - 6^7 + 7^7 + 7^7 - 3^7}{1^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 6^0 - 7^0 - 7^0 - 3^0}$$

$$1619635 := \frac{-1^7 + 6^7 - 1^7 + 9^7 - 6^7 - 3^7 + 5^7}{1^0 + 6^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 - 3^0 - 5^0}$$

$$1625221 := \frac{-1^9 + 6^9 + 2^9 - 5^9 + 2^9 + 2^9 - 1^9}{1^0 + 6^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 - 1^0}$$

$$1741725 := \frac{1^7 + 7^7 + 4^7 + 1^7 + 7^7 + 2^7 + 5^7}{1^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 - 7^0 - 2^0 - 5^0}$$

$$1798345 := \frac{-1^7 - 7^7 + 9^7 - 8^7 - 3^7 + 4^7 - 5^7}{1^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 - 3^0 - 4^0 - 5^0}$$

$$1831416 := \frac{1^7 + 8^7 - 3^7 + 1^7 + 4^7 + 1^7 - 6^7}{1^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 1^0 - 4^0 - 1^0 - 6^0}$$

$$1836869 := \frac{1^8 - 8^8 + 3^8 + 6^8 - 8^8 + 6^8 + 9^8}{1^0 + 8^0 + 3^0 + 6^0 + 8^0 + 6^0 + 9^0}$$

$$1837568 := \frac{1^8 + 8^8 + 3^8 - 7^8 - 5^8 - 6^8 + 8^8}{-1^1 + 8^1 - 3^1 + 7^1 + 5^1 + 6^1 - 8^1}$$

$$1863444 := \frac{-1^8 + 8^8 - 6^8 + 3^8 - 4^8 - 4^8 - 4^8}{1^1 + 8^1 + 6^1 - 3^1 + 4^1 - 4^1 - 4^1}$$

$$1871417 := \frac{1^8 + 8^8 + 7^8 + 1^8 + 4^8 - 1^8 - 7^8}{-1^1 + 8^1 + 7^1 - 1^1 + 4^1 - 1^1 - 7^1}$$

$$1872189 := \frac{1^9 - 8^9 - 7^9 + 2^9 - 1^9 - 8^9 + 9^9}{1^3 - 8^3 + 7^3 - 2^3 + 1^3 - 8^3 + 9^3}$$

$$1873726 := \frac{-1^8 + 8^8 + 7^8 - 3^8 + 7^8 - 2^8 + 6^8}{-1^1 + 8^1 + 7^1 + 3^1 + 7^1 - 2^1 - 6^1}$$

$$1915536 := \frac{-1^8 + 9^8 - 1^8 + 5^8 + 5^8 - 3^8 - 6^8}{1^1 + 9^1 - 1^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 - 3^1 + 6^1}$$

$$1956869 := \frac{-1^7 + 9^7 + 5^7 + 6^7 + 8^7 - 6^7 + 9^7}{-1^1 - 9^1 + 5^1 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 6^1 - 9^1}$$

$$1960686 := \frac{-1^9 + 9^9 + 6^9 - 0^9 - 6^9 - 8^9 - 6^9}{-1^2 + 9^2 + 6^2 - 0^2 + 6^2 - 8^2 + 6^2}$$

$$2058218 := \frac{2^7 - 0^7 - 5^7 + 8^7 + 2^7 + 1^7 + 8^7}{-2^1 - 0^1 + 5^1 + 8^1 - 2^1 + 1^1 - 8^1}$$

$$2155785 := \frac{-2^8 - 1^8 + 5^8 + 5^8 + 7^8 + 8^8 + 5^8}{2^1 - 1^1 + 5^1 - 5^1 + 7^1 + 8^1 - 5^1}$$

$$2175278 := \frac{2^7 + 1^7 + 7^7 + 5^7 - 2^7 - 7^7 + 8^7}{2^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 - 2^0 - 7^0 - 8^0}$$

$$2263085 := \frac{2^9 - 2^9 - 6^9 + 3^9 - 0^9 + 8^9 - 5^9}{-2^2 - 2^2 - 6^2 + 3^2 - 0^2 + 8^2 + 5^2}$$

$$2298234 := \frac{2^7 + 2^7 + 9^7 + 8^7 + 2^7 - 3^7 + 4^7}{2^0 + 2^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 2^0 - 3^0 - 4^0}$$

$$2316084 := \frac{-2^8 + 3^8 - 1^8 + 6^8 - 0^8 + 8^8 + 4^8}{2^1 - 3^1 - 1^1 + 6^1 - 0^1 + 8^1 - 4^1}$$

$$2329710 := \frac{2^8 - 3^8 - 2^8 + 9^8 - 7^8 + 1^8 - 0^8}{2^1 - 3^1 + 2^1 + 9^1 + 7^1 - 1^1 - 0^1}$$

$$2351393 := \frac{2^7 + 3^7 - 5^7 + 1^7 - 3^7 + 9^7 - 3^7}{2^1 + 3^1 + 5^1 + 1^1 + 3^1 - 9^1 - 3^1}$$

$$2358645 := \frac{2^7 - 3^7 + 5^7 + 8^7 + 6^7 - 4^7 - 5^7}{2^0 + 3^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 - 6^0 - 4^0 - 5^0}$$

$$2391120 := \frac{2^8 - 3^8 + 9^8 + 1^8 - 1^8 - 2^8 - 0^8}{2^1 + 3^1 + 9^1 + 1^1 + 1^1 + 2^1 - 0^1}$$

$$2391999 := \frac{-2^7 + 3^7 + 9^7 - 1^7 + 9^7 + 9^7 - 9^7}{2^1 + 3^1 + 9^1 - 1^1 + 9^1 - 9^1 - 9^1}$$

$$2434120 := \frac{-2^{12} + 4^{12} + 3^{12} + 4^{12} - 1^{12} - 2^{12} - 0^{12}}{2^1 + 4^1 + 3^1 + 4^1 - 1^1 + 2^1 - 0^1}$$

$$2441151 := \frac{-2^{10} + 4^{10} - 4^{10} + 1^{10} + 1^{10} + 5^{10} + 1^{10}}{2^1 + 4^1 + 4^1 + 1^1 - 1^1 - 5^1 - 1^1}$$

$$2453844 := \frac{2^9 + 4^9 - 5^9 - 3^9 + 8^9 + 4^9 - 4^9}{2^2 - 4^2 + 5^2 + 3^2 + 8^2 - 4^2 - 4^2}$$

$$2467805 := \frac{2^8 + 4^8 + 6^8 + 7^8 + 8^8 - 0^8 + 5^8}{2^1 + 4^1 - 6^1 + 7^1 + 8^1 - 0^1 - 5^1}$$

$$2479334 := \frac{2^9 + 4^9 - 7^9 + 9^9 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 4^9}{-2^2 + 4^2 + 7^2 + 9^2 - 3^2 - 3^2 + 4^2}$$

$$2488123 := \frac{2^9 + 4^9 + 8^9 + 8^9 + 1^9 - 2^9 + 3^9}{2^3 + 4^3 + 8^3 - 8^3 + 1^3 + 2^3 + 3^3}$$

$$2521318 := \frac{2^9 + 5^9 - 2^9 + 1^9 - 3^9 + 1^9 + 8^9}{2^2 - 5^2 + 2^2 - 1^2 + 3^2 - 1^2 + 8^2}$$

$$2638700 := \frac{2^7 - 6^7 - 3^7 + 8^7 + 7^7 - 0^7 - 0^7}{2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 - 7^0 - 0^0 - 0^0}$$

$$2638701 := \frac{2^7 - 6^7 - 3^7 + 8^7 + 7^7 - 0^7 + 1^7}{2^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 - 7^0 - 0^0 - 1^0}$$

$$2754495 := \frac{-2^9 - 7^9 + 5^9 + 4^9 - 4^9 + 9^9 - 5^9}{-2^2 + 7^2 + 5^2 + 4^2 - 4^2 + 9^2 - 5^2}$$

$$2785244 := \frac{-2^8 + 7^8 + 8^8 - 5^8 - 2^8 + 4^8 + 4^8}{-2^1 + 7^1 + 8^1 + 5^1 - 2^1 - 4^1 - 4^1}$$

$$2824077 := \frac{-2^8 + 8^8 - 2^8 - 4^8 - 0^8 + 7^8 + 7^8}{2^1 - 8^1 - 2^1 + 4^1 - 0^1 + 7^1 + 7^1}$$

$$2856837 := \frac{-2^9 + 8^9 + 5^9 - 6^9 + 8^9 + 3^9 - 7^9}{-2^2 + 8^2 - 5^2 + 6^2 + 8^2 - 3^2 - 7^2}$$

$$2918379 := \frac{-2^7 + 9^7 - 1^7 + 8^7 - 3^7 + 7^7 - 9^7}{2^0 + 9^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 - 3^0 - 7^0 - 9^0}$$

$$2963821 := \frac{2^7 + 9^7 + 6^7 - 3^7 - 8^7 + 2^7 - 1^7}{2^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 - 8^0 - 2^0 - 1^0}$$

$$2974885 := \frac{-2^9 + 9^9 - 7^9 - 4^9 - 8^9 - 8^9 + 5^9}{2^1 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 4^1 + 8^1 - 8^1 + 5^1}$$

$$3071153 := \frac{-3^8 - 0^8 + 7^8 + 1^8 + 1^8 + 5^8 - 3^8}{3^1 - 0^1 + 7^1 + 1^1 - 1^1 - 5^1 - 3^1}$$

$$3169287 := \frac{3^7 + 1^7 + 6^7 + 9^7 - 2^7 + 8^7 - 7^7}{3^1 + 1^1 + 6^1 + 9^1 - 2^1 - 8^1 - 7^1}$$

$$3177059 := \frac{3^7 + 1^7 + 7^7 + 7^7 - 0^7 - 5^7 + 9^7}{3^1 - 1^1 + 7^1 + 7^1 - 0^1 - 5^1 - 9^1}$$

$$3194922 := \frac{3^7 + 1^7 + 9^7 + 4^7 + 9^7 + 2^7 + 2^7}{3^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 4^0 + 9^0 - 2^0 - 2^0}$$

$$3276825 := \frac{-3^7 + 2^7 + 7^7 + 6^7 + 8^7 + 2^7 + 5^7}{3^0 + 2^0 + 7^0 + 6^0 - 8^0 - 2^0 - 5^0}$$

$$3295471 := \frac{3^{10} - 2^{10} + 9^{10} + 5^{10} - 4^{10} - 7^{10} - 1^{10}}{-3^3 - 2^3 + 9^3 - 5^3 + 4^3 + 7^3 - 1^3}$$

$$3299045 := \frac{3^8 + 2^8 + 9^8 + 9^8 - 0^8 + 4^8 - 5^8}{-3^1 + 2^1 + 9^1 + 9^1 - 0^1 + 4^1 + 5^1}$$

$$3354947 := \frac{3^8 + 3^8 - 5^8 + 4^8 + 9^8 - 4^8 - 7^8}{3^1 + 3^1 - 5^1 + 4^1 + 9^1 + 4^1 - 7^1}$$

$$3378696 := \frac{3^8 - 3^8 - 7^8 + 8^8 + 6^8 + 9^8 - 6^8}{3^1 + 3^1 - 7^1 + 8^1 + 6^1 + 9^1 - 6^1}$$

$$3465999 := \frac{3^8 - 4^8 + 6^8 + 5^8 + 9^8 + 9^8 - 9^8}{-3^1 - 4^1 + 6^1 + 5^1 + 9^1 + 9^1 - 9^1}$$

$$3478627 := \frac{-3^7 + 4^7 + 7^7 + 8^7 - 6^7 + 2^7 + 7^7}{3^0 + 4^0 + 7^0 + 8^0 - 6^0 - 2^0 - 7^0}$$

$$3589386 := \frac{-3^8 - 5^8 - 8^8 + 9^8 - 3^8 - 8^8 + 6^8}{3^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 3^0 - 8^0 - 6^0}$$

$$3605739 := \frac{3^7 - 6^7 - 0^7 - 5^7 - 7^7 + 3^7 + 9^7}{3^0 + 6^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 - 7^0 - 3^0 - 9^0}$$

$$3629482 := \frac{-3^8 - 6^8 - 2^8 + 9^8 - 4^8 + 8^8 - 2^8}{-3^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 + 9^1 - 4^1 + 8^1 - 2^1}$$

$$3638806 := \frac{3^7 - 6^7 + 3^7 + 8^7 + 8^7 - 0^7 - 6^7}{3^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 - 8^0 - 0^0 - 6^0}$$

$$3874393 := \frac{3^9 - 8^9 - 7^9 + 4^9 - 3^9 + 9^9 - 3^9}{-3^2 - 8^2 + 7^2 + 4^2 - 3^2 + 9^2 - 3^2}$$

$$3892429 := \frac{-3^7 + 8^7 + 9^7 + 2^7 + 4^7 - 2^7 + 9^7}{3^0 + 8^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 4^0 - 2^0 - 9^0}$$

$$3963672 := \frac{3^7 + 9^7 + 6^7 + 3^7 - 6^7 - 7^7 - 2^7}{3^0 + 9^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 - 6^0 - 7^0 - 2^0}$$

$$4062541 := \frac{4^9 - 0^9 + 6^9 + 2^9 - 5^9 - 4^9 - 1^9}{4^1 - 0^1 + 6^1 + 2^1 - 5^1 - 4^1 - 1^1}$$

$$4091751 := \frac{-4^8 - 0^8 + 9^8 + 1^8 - 7^8 - 5^8 - 1^8}{4^1 - 0^1 + 9^1 - 1^1 - 7^1 + 5^1 - 1^1}$$

$$4210818 := \frac{4^7 + 2^7 + 1^7 - 0^7 + 8^7 + 1^7 + 8^7}{4^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 0^0 - 8^0 - 1^0 - 8^0}$$

$$4263782 := \frac{-4^{10} + 2^{10} + 6^{10} - 3^{10} + 7^{10} + 8^{10} - 2^{10}}{-4^3 - 2^3 + 6^3 + 3^3 - 7^3 + 8^3 - 2^3}$$

$$4273376 := \frac{4^{13} + 2^{13} + 7^{13} + 3^{13} - 3^{13} - 7^{13} + 6^{13}}{-4^4 - 2^4 + 7^4 - 3^4 - 3^4 + 7^4 - 6^4}$$

$$4368953 := \frac{4^8 - 3^8 + 6^8 + 8^8 + 9^8 - 5^8 - 3^8}{-4^1 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 8^1 + 9^1 - 5^1 - 3^1}$$

$$4428864 := \frac{4^8 + 4^8 + 2^8 + 8^8 + 8^8 + 6^8 + 4^8}{4^1 - 4^1 + 2^1 + 8^1 + 8^1 - 6^1 - 4^1}$$

$$4467745 := \frac{-4^8 - 4^8 + 6^8 + 7^8 + 7^8 - 4^8 + 5^8}{4^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 + 7^0 + 7^0 - 4^0 - 5^0}$$

$$4473519 := \frac{4^8 - 4^8 + 7^8 + 3^8 + 5^8 + 1^8 + 9^8}{4^1 + 4^1 - 7^1 - 3^1 + 5^1 - 1^1 + 9^1}$$

$$4500168 := \frac{-4^8 - 5^8 - 0^8 - 0^8 + 1^8 + 6^8 + 8^8}{-4^1 + 5^1 - 0^1 - 0^1 + 1^1 - 6^1 + 8^1}$$

$$4563887 := \frac{-4^9 + 5^9 - 6^9 - 3^9 + 8^9 - 8^9 + 7^9}{4^0 + 5^0 + 6^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 8^0 + 7^0}$$

$$4608657 := \frac{4^9 + 6^9 - 0^9 + 8^9 - 6^9 - 5^9 - 7^9}{4^1 + 6^1 - 0^1 - 8^1 + 6^1 + 5^1 + 7^1}$$

$$4612215 := \frac{-4^{10} + 6^{10} + 1^{10} + 2^{10} - 2^{10} - 1^{10} + 5^{10}}{4^1 + 6^1 + 1^1 + 2^1 - 2^1 - 1^1 + 5^1}$$

$$4724430 := \frac{4^{10} + 7^{10} + 2^{10} + 4^{10} - 4^{10} - 3^{10} - 0^{10}}{4^2 + 7^2 + 2^2 + 4^2 - 4^2 - 3^2 - 0^2}$$

$$4856643 := \frac{4^9 + 8^9 + 5^9 - 6^9 - 6^9 + 4^9 + 3^9}{4^1 + 8^1 + 5^1 + 6^1 - 6^1 + 4^1 + 3^1}$$

$$4883946 := \frac{-4^8 + 8^8 + 8^8 - 3^8 + 9^8 - 4^8 + 6^8}{4^1 + 8^1 + 8^1 - 3^1 + 9^1 - 4^1 - 6^1}$$

$$4884864 := \frac{4^8 + 8^8 + 8^8 + 4^8 + 8^8 - 6^8 + 4^8}{4^1 + 8^1 + 8^1 - 4^1 - 8^1 + 6^1 - 4^1}$$

$$4906183 := \frac{-4^8 + 9^8 - 0^8 - 6^8 + 1^8 - 8^8 + 3^8}{4^0 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 6^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 - 3^0}$$

$$4922617 := \frac{4^9 + 9^9 - 2^9 - 2^9 + 6^9 + 1^9 + 7^9}{-4^3 + 9^3 - 2^3 - 2^3 - 6^3 - 1^3 - 7^3}$$

$$5170377 := \frac{-5^{10} + 1^{10} + 7^{10} - 0^{10} - 3^{10} + 7^{10} + 7^{10}}{5^2 - 1^2 + 7^2 - 0^2 - 3^2 + 7^2 + 7^2}$$

$$5374432 := \frac{-5^8 + 3^8 + 7^8 + 4^8 - 4^8 - 3^8 + 2^8}{5^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 4^0 - 4^0 - 3^0 - 2^0}$$

$$5417495 := \frac{-5^7 - 4^7 + 1^7 + 7^7 - 4^7 + 9^7 - 5^7}{5^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 7^0 - 4^0 - 9^0 - 5^0}$$

$$5418421 := \frac{-5^8 - 4^8 + 1^8 + 8^8 - 4^8 - 2^8 - 1^8}{5^0 + 4^0 + 1^0 + 8^0 + 4^0 - 2^0 - 1^0}$$

$$5793095 := \frac{5^8 - 7^8 + 9^8 - 3^8 - 0^8 + 9^8 + 5^8}{5^1 - 7^1 + 9^1 + 3^1 - 0^1 + 9^1 - 5^1}$$

$$5928243 := \frac{5^9 + 9^9 + 2^9 - 8^9 + 2^9 - 4^9 + 3^9}{5^2 + 9^2 + 2^2 - 8^2 + 2^2 - 4^2 + 3^2}$$

$$6010696 := \frac{6^8 - 0^8 - 1^8 - 0^8 + 6^8 + 9^8 + 6^8}{6^1 - 0^1 - 1^1 - 0^1 + 6^1 - 9^1 + 6^1}$$

$$6075136 := \frac{-6^9 - 0^9 + 7^9 - 5^9 + 1^9 - 3^9 - 6^9}{6^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 + 5^0 + 1^0 - 3^0 - 6^0}$$

$$6140169 := \frac{6^8 - 1^8 - 4^8 - 0^8 - 1^8 - 6^8 + 9^8}{6^0 + 1^0 + 4^0 + 0^0 + 1^0 + 6^0 + 9^0}$$

$$6151253 := \frac{6^9 + 1^9 - 5^9 + 1^9 - 2^9 - 5^9 - 3^9}{6^0 + 1^0 + 5^0 + 1^0 - 2^0 - 5^0 - 3^0}$$

$$6187825 := \frac{6^{10} - 1^{10} + 8^{10} + 7^{10} - 8^{10} - 2^{10} + 5^{10}}{6^2 + 1^2 + 8^2 + 7^2 - 8^2 - 2^2 - 5^2}$$

$$6350645 := \frac{6^{11} + 3^{11} + 5^{11} - 0^{11} + 6^{11} - 4^{11} + 5^{11}}{6^2 - 3^2 + 5^2 - 0^2 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 5^2}$$

$$6503489 := \frac{-6^7 - 5^7 - 0^7 - 3^7 - 4^7 + 8^7 + 9^7}{6^0 + 5^0 + 0^0 + 3^0 - 4^0 - 8^0 - 9^0}$$

$$6531701 := \frac{6^{10} - 5^{10} - 3^{10} + 1^{10} + 7^{10} - 0^{10} - 1^{10}}{6^2 - 5^2 - 3^2 + 1^2 + 7^2 - 0^2 - 1^2}$$

$$6642413 := \frac{6^{11} + 6^{11} - 4^{11} - 2^{11} - 4^{11} + 1^{11} + 3^{11}}{6^2 + 6^2 + 4^2 - 2^2 + 4^2 - 1^2 + 3^2}$$

$$6646623 := \frac{6^8 + 6^8 - 4^8 + 6^8 + 6^8 + 2^8 - 3^8}{6^0 + 6^0 + 4^0 + 6^0 - 6^0 - 2^0 - 3^0}$$

$$6707932 := \frac{6^7 + 7^7 - 0^7 + 7^7 + 9^7 - 3^7 + 2^7}{6^0 + 7^0 + 0^0 + 7^0 - 9^0 - 3^0 - 2^0}$$

$$6725516 := \frac{6^9 + 7^9 - 2^9 + 5^9 - 5^9 + 1^9 - 6^9}{-6^1 + 7^1 + 2^1 + 5^1 + 5^1 - 1^1 - 6^1}$$

$$6732192 := \frac{-6^8 + 7^8 - 3^8 + 2^8 - 1^8 + 9^8 - 2^8}{6^0 + 7^0 + 3^0 + 2^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 2^0}$$

$$6977583 := \frac{-6^9 + 9^9 - 7^9 - 7^9 - 5^9 - 8^9 + 3^9}{6^1 + 9^1 + 7^1 + 7^1 + 5^1 - 8^1 - 3^1}$$

$$7051122 := \frac{7^9 - 0^9 + 5^9 + 1^9 - 1^9 + 2^9 - 2^9}{7^1 - 0^1 + 5^1 - 1^1 - 1^1 - 2^1 - 2^1}$$

$$7123259 := \frac{-7^9 + 1^9 + 2^9 + 3^9 - 2^9 + 5^9 + 9^9}{-7^2 + 1^2 + 2^2 - 3^2 - 2^2 + 5^2 + 9^2}$$

$$7125634 := \frac{7^8 + 1^8 - 2^8 - 5^8 + 6^8 + 3^8 + 4^8}{7^0 + 1^0 + 2^0 + 5^0 - 6^0 - 3^0 - 4^0}$$

$$7181524 := \frac{7^9 - 1^9 + 8^9 - 1^9 - 5^9 + 2^9 - 4^9}{7^1 + 1^1 + 8^1 + 1^1 + 5^1 - 2^1 + 4^1}$$

$$7198586 := \frac{-7^8 + 1^8 + 9^8 + 8^8 + 5^8 - 8^8 - 6^8}{7^0 + 1^0 + 9^0 + 8^0 + 5^0 + 8^0 - 6^0}$$

$$7379571 := \frac{7^8 + 3^8 - 7^8 + 9^8 - 5^8 - 7^8 - 1^8}{7^0 + 3^0 + 7^0 + 9^0 + 5^0 + 7^0 - 1^0}$$

$$7387625 := \frac{-7^{10} - 3^{10} + 8^{10} - 7^{10} - 6^{10} + 2^{10} + 5^{10}}{7^2 - 3^2 + 8^2 - 7^2 + 6^2 - 2^2 - 5^2}$$

$$7390054 := \frac{-7^8 - 3^8 + 9^8 - 0^8 - 0^8 - 5^8 + 4^8}{7^0 + 3^0 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 0^0 + 5^0 - 4^0}$$

$$7444416 := \frac{7^8 + 4^8 + 4^8 - 4^8 - 4^8 - 1^8 + 6^8}{7^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 + 4^0 - 4^0 - 1^0 - 6^0}$$

$$7561867 := \frac{-7^{10} - 5^{10} - 6^{10} + 1^{10} + 8^{10} - 6^{10} - 7^{10}}{7^3 - 5^3 + 6^3 + 1^3 - 8^3 - 6^3 + 7^3}$$

$$7618737 := \frac{7^9 - 6^9 - 1^9 + 8^9 - 7^9 + 3^9 - 7^9}{7^1 + 6^1 + 1^1 + 8^1 - 7^1 + 3^1 - 7^1}$$

$$7687912 := \frac{7^8 + 6^8 + 8^8 - 7^8 + 9^8 - 1^8 - 2^8}{7^1 - 6^1 + 8^1 - 7^1 + 9^1 - 1^1 - 2^1}$$

$$7822010 := \frac{-7^9 + 8^9 + 2^9 - 2^9 - 0^9 - 1^9 - 0^9}{7^1 + 8^1 - 2^1 - 2^1 - 0^1 + 1^1 - 0^1}$$

$$7860812 := \frac{7^9 + 8^9 - 6^9 - 0^9 + 8^9 + 1^9 - 2^9}{-7^2 + 8^2 - 6^2 - 0^2 + 8^2 - 1^2 - 2^2}$$

$$8154157 := \frac{8^9 + 1^9 - 5^9 - 4^9 - 1^9 - 5^9 - 7^9}{8^1 + 1^1 + 5^1 - 4^1 - 1^1 - 5^1 + 7^1}$$

$$8157924 := \frac{8^8 - 1^8 - 5^8 + 7^8 + 9^8 - 2^8 + 4^8}{8^1 - 1^1 + 5^1 - 7^1 + 9^1 - 2^1 - 4^1}$$

$$8364807 := \frac{8^9 + 3^9 + 6^9 - 4^9 - 8^9 - 0^9 + 7^9}{8^1 + 3^1 + 6^1 + 4^1 - 8^1 - 0^1 - 7^1}$$

$$8391889 := \frac{8^8 + 3^8 + 9^8 + 1^8 + 8^8 - 8^8 - 9^8}{8^1 - 3^1 - 9^1 - 1^1 + 8^1 + 8^1 - 9^1}$$

$$8421120 := \frac{8^8 + 4^8 - 2^8 + 1^8 - 1^8 - 2^8 - 0^8}{8^1 - 4^1 + 2^1 - 1^1 - 1^1 - 2^1 - 0^1}$$

$$8694375 := \frac{8^9 - 6^9 + 9^9 + 4^9 - 3^9 - 7^9 - 5^9}{-8^2 + 6^2 + 9^2 + 4^2 + 3^2 - 7^2 + 5^2}$$

$$8741936 := \frac{8^8 - 7^8 + 4^8 - 1^8 + 9^8 + 3^8 - 6^8}{8^1 - 7^1 + 4^1 + 1^1 + 9^1 - 3^1 - 6^1}$$

$$9245686 := \frac{9^9 - 2^9 - 4^9 - 5^9 - 6^9 + 8^9 - 6^9}{9^2 - 2^2 + 4^2 + 5^2 + 6^2 - 8^2 - 6^2}$$

$$9264867 := \frac{9^{10} - 2^{10} - 6^{10} + 4^{10} - 8^{10} - 6^{10} + 7^{10}}{9^2 - 2^2 + 6^2 + 4^2 + 8^2 + 6^2 + 7^2}$$

$$9432752 := \frac{9^8 + 4^8 - 3^8 - 2^8 - 7^8 + 5^8 - 2^8}{9^1 + 4^1 + 3^1 + 2^1 - 7^1 - 5^1 - 2^1}$$

$$9664812 := \frac{9^9 + 6^9 - 6^9 + 4^9 + 8^9 - 1^9 - 2^9}{9^2 - 6^2 - 6^2 - 4^2 + 8^2 + 1^2 - 2^2}$$

$$9800817 := \frac{9^7 + 8^7 - 0^7 - 0^7 + 8^7 + 1^7 + 7^7}{9^0 + 8^0 + 0^0 + 0^0 - 8^0 - 1^0 - 7^0}$$

$$9832465 := \frac{9^9 - 8^9 - 3^9 + 2^9 + 4^9 + 6^9 + 5^9}{9^1 + 8^1 + 3^1 + 2^1 + 4^1 + 6^1 - 5^1}$$

$$9901381 := \frac{9^8 + 9^8 - 0^8 + 1^8 - 3^8 - 8^8 + 1^8}{9^0 + 9^0 + 0^0 + 1^0 + 3^0 + 8^0 + 1^0}$$

$$9926315 := \frac{9^7 + 9^7 + 2^7 + 6^7 + 3^7 + 1^7 + 5^7}{9^0 + 9^0 + 2^0 + 6^0 - 3^0 - 1^0 - 5^0}$$

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